

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases

Base 12 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{6853_{10} \quad 3B71_{12}}} \\ -1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^{6_{12}+7_{12}}*89A_{12}+B_{12} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{419_{10} \quad 2AB_{12}}} \\ B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12} \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\underline{\underline{-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}+7_{10}}*1270_{10}+11_{10}}} \qquad \underline{\underline{11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}}}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 A B + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to B occur in increasing or decreasing order:

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+B}} \qquad \underline{\underline{B+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21}}$$

Digits represent single-digit or multi-digit numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+B}} \qquad \underline{\underline{B+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21}}$$

Numbers occur in positive form or negative form (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+B}} \qquad \underline{\underline{B+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21}}$$

Allowed operations; addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and/or exponentiation.

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+B}} \qquad \underline{\underline{B+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21}}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by parentheses (also nested parentheses).

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+B}} \qquad \underline{\underline{B+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21}}$$

Representations with negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{(1+2-3)*(45^{-(6^7)}+8-9AB)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(BA98+7^{-(6^5)}+4)*(3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9AB)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(BA98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1+2-3)*(45^{-(6^7)}+8-9AB)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(BA98+7^{-(6^5)}+4)*(3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(-(1+2)+3)*(45^{(6^7)}+8-9AB)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(BA98+7^{(6^5)}+4)*(-(3-2)+1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9))*AB)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{-(BA*(9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)}} \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 12 crazy sequential representations for 0000_{12} up to $BBBB_{12}$

Expected number of representations = $2_{12} + BBBB_{12} + BBBB_{12} = 20000_{12} = 41472_{10}$

Results

41465_{10} out of 41472_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing	B039, B264, B647, B860, B909, B933, B934
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Decreasing	None
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Notes

Authors consider base 12 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Other Bases

Authors also identified genuine crazy sequential representations for other bases:

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

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Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

Supplement 1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0000	00000	$(1+2-3)^*(456789AB)$	$BA987654^*(3-2-1)$
0001	00001	$1+2-3-4+5^*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5-4-3^*2^*1$
0002	00002	$12+3+45-6-78-(-9-A-B)$	$-B+A+98+7-65-4-32-1$
0003	00003	$12-(-3+4+5)+6+7-(-8+9-A+B)$	$-B-(A+9)+87-(6+54-(-3+2+1))$
0004	00004	$123-4+56+7-89-AB$	$-B-A-9+8+7+6-5-4-3+21$
0005	00005	$-123-4-5+67+89-(A-B)$	$BA-9-(87+65)-(-43-2+1)$
0006	00006	$1-2-3+4+5-6+7+8-9-A+B$	$BA-9+87-65-43^*(2+1)$
0007	00007	$1^*2-3+45+6+7^*8-(9A-B)$	$BA-9-(87+65-43)-(-2-1)$
0008	00008	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7-89-(A-B)$	$BA-9+8-(76-5)-(43-2-1)$
0009	00009	$123+4-56-78-9-(A-B)$	$BA-9-8-76-54+32^*1$
000A	00010	$1-(-2+3+4)-(-56-7)-(-89+AB)$	$B-A-(-9+8)^*(7-6)^*5+4-3+2+1$
000B	00011	$1-(-2-3^*4)-56-(-78+9)-A-B$	$B-(-A9-(-8-(76+5+43-21)))$
0010	00012	$1-2-3-4-(5-(6-7))-(-8^*9-AB)$	$B+A9-8-76-(-5-(4-32)+1)$
0011	00013	$12-3+4+56-7-8+9-A-B$	$B-A-9+87-65-(4+3)-2^*-1$
0012	00014	$1+23-45+6+7-89+AB$	$-BA+9+87+65+4-(32-1)$
0013	00015	$-1+2+3+4-5-6+7+8-9A+B$	$-B+A-98+76+5-4^*-3+21$
0014	00016	$-1-23+4-5+(-6+78)^*(-9-A)+B$	$-B+A9-(87-65+43+21)$
0015	00017	$12+3-45+6+7^*8-9^*(A+B)$	$-B+A-98+7+65+43-2+1$
0016	00018	$-1+23+4-56-7-89-AB$	$-BA-(-98-7-6-5-43+21)$
0017	00019	$-12-3-4-5-6+7+8-9-A+B$	$B-A-(-98+76)-(5+4)-(-3-2^*-1)$
0018	00020	$1^*-2+3+4+56-(78-9-A+B)$	$B+A^*-9^*-87-6-5432-1$
0019	00021	$-12+3-4+56+78+9-AB$	$B+A98-765-(4+321)$
001A	00022	$-12+3+4-5-(-67-(8+9A-B))$	$-B-A+98+7+6-5-4-(-3+21)$
001B	00023	$-12-(-3-4+5)-(67+8+9-AB)$	$-B+A-9-(8+7)-(-6-5-4)-(-3+21)$
0020	00024	$-1^*(2-3^*(4+5^*6)-(78-9+A+B))$	$-B+A+9+8-7-6-5-4-3^*2+1$
0021	00025	$12-3-4^*(-5-6)+7+8+9-AB$	$-B+A9+8-7^*6-5+3+2^*1$
0022	00026	$1-(2-3+4+5-6+7+8+9^*A-B)$	$B+A-(-9-8+7+6)-5-4-(32-1)$
0023	00027	$12-3-(45+6+7-8)-(-9-AB)$	$-B-(-A-98+7+65)-4-(-3+2+1)$
0024	00028	$12+3+45+6+78-9AB$	$B-(A+9-(-8-(-7-6)))-(-5-4+3-21)$
0025	00029	$-12+3+4-5+6+7+8+9-A+B$	$B-(A-98+76)+5-(-4^*(-3+2)-1)$
0026	00030	$-12-3-4-(-56-78)-(9A-B)$	$-B+A^*-9+8-7+65-(-43+2^*-1)$
0027	00031	$-1-(2+3)-(-4-56+7)-(-89+AB)$	$-B+A^*9-8^*(7-65-(-43-21))$
0028	00032	$1-(2-3)-(-45-6+7-89-(-A-B))$	$-B+A+9+8^*-7-(-65-4)-3-2^*-1$
0029	00033	$-1-23-(-4-5)-(67^*(-8+9)-AB)$	$BA-9+8-7-65+4-3-21$
002A	00034	$1-(-2-3+4)-(-5^*6-7+8+9+A+B)$	$-B+A9-(8+76-5-4-(-3-2^*-1))$
002B	00035	$12-3+4+56-7-(8-9)-A+B$	$B-A-(9-8+7-6)-(5+3+2+1)$
0030	00036	$-1-2-3^*(-4-56+78-9)^*(A-B)$	$-BA+9+87-(-6-(5-4-3))-(-2-1)$
0031	00037	$-1-(2-3+4)-(56-7-(8^*-9+AB))$	$-B-A-(-98+7+65-43+21)$
0032	00038	$123+4-5^*(-6+7)+8-9-AB$	$-B-(-A9-8-7-6+5+4+32-1)$
0033	00039	$-12-(-3-4)-(-5-6-7^*-8)-(9^*-A-B)$	$B-(-A9-(8-7)+65)-(-4-(3^*-2-1))$
0034	00040	$-1+23+45-6-7+89-AB$	$BA-9+87-(6-5+4^*-3+2^*-1)$
0035	00041	$1-(-2-3)-4-(-5^*(-6-7)-(89+A))-B$	$-BA+9+87+65-4-3+2-1$
0036	00042	$-1-23-(-45+6+7+8^*(9-A-B))$	$-B+A+9-(8^*7-(-6-5))-(-43^*-2+1)$
0037	00043	$-1+2-3+4+5+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9-8+7-6^*-5+43-21$
0038	00044	$-12-(-3-4-56-(78-9A+B))$	$B-(-A-98-(-76-5-4-(-3-2-1)))$
0039	00045	$-1-(23-4-56-7-8-9+A+B)$	$-BA-9-8-7-6+5+4^*3+21$
003A	00046	$123+45-6+7+8-9A+B$	$BA+9-8-7-6-5-4^*-3-21$
003B	00047	$-1+23-4+5+6+7-8^*-9-AB$	$-B+A9+8-(-7-6+5+4+3+21)$
0040	00048	$-12+3+4+5+6+7-8-9+A+B$	$-BA-9+8+76-(-5-4-32)-1$
0041	00049	$12+3-4+5+6+7+8+9-AB$	$-B-A+9+87-65-4+32+1$
0042	00050	$1-2-(3+4-5^*-6-7+8+9-AB)$	$-BA9+876-(-5-4-321)$
0043	00051	$1+2+3+4-5-6-7-89+AB$	$B-(-A9+87-(6+5)^*(4-3)-(-2+1))$
0044	00052	$-12+3+4-56-7-8-(-9A+B)$	$B+A-(9-8)+7-65-43^*-2^*1$
0045	00053	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+89-AB$	$B-A-9-8+7+6+5+43+21$
0046	00054	$-1+23+4-5+6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA-9-8-7-6-5-4+32+1$
0047	00055	$-1+2+3+4-(56-78)-(-9+A)-B$	$B-A-9-(8^*-7+(-6-5)^*4+32-1)$
0048	00056	$12-3-4+5+6-7-(8-9A)-B$	$-B-(-A9-8-(-7-6-5-(43+2)+1))$
0049	00057	$1+23-4-(-56+7)+89-AB$	$B-A-9+87-6+5-(4^*3+21)$
004A	00058	$-1+2-(3-4)-56+7+8+9-(-A-B)$	$-B-A+98-7+6-5+4+3+21$
004B	00059	$-1^*(2+3+4-5+6-7+8-9+A-B)$	$BA-(98-76)-(5+43)-(-2-1)$
0050	00060	$-12+3-4-56-7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A9-8-76+5-4+32+1$
0051	00061	$-1+2-3-4-5+6+7-89+AB$	$-BA+98+7+65-4-3^*-2+1$
0052	00062	$-12-(-3+4+56-78-9A-B)$	$B+A9-87-6+5+43-21$
0053	00063	$-12+3^*(-4+5)+6+7+8+9+A^*-B$	$B-(-A-9)-(-8+7^*6)-(-5-4-3)^*(2-1)$
0054	00064	$-1-23-4+56-78-9+AB$	$-B-A9+87-6+5+43^*2^*1$
0055	00065	$12+3-(45-6+7-8^*-9-AB)$	$-BA+98+76-(-5+4^*(-3+2)^*-1)$
0056	00066	$-1+23+4+5+6-(-7-89)-AB$	$B+A9-8-(-7+6-(-5-4-3^*(2-1)))$
0057	00067	$123-45+6+7-8-(-9+AB)$	$-B+A-9+87+65-43^*2-1$
0058	00068	$-1-2+3+4-5-6+7-(-8-9)+AB$	$B-A-(9-8+7+6-5+4)-(-3+21)$
0059	00069	$-12-3+4-5+6-(-78-9-A-B)$	$BA-98+7+65-4-32+1$
005A	00070	$12-3+4+5+6+7-(-8^*-9-AB)$	$B-A-(-9+87)-(-6-5-4^*32^*1)$
005B	00071	$-1-2-3+4-5^*(-6+7)-(89+A+B)$	$B+A9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3-21)$
0060	00072	$12-(-3-4)-(-56-7+8+9A-B)$	$B-(-A+9+8+7-6-5-4+3-(-2-1))$
0061	00073	$-1+23-4+5+6+7+8-9-A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7+6+5+4-(32-1)$
0062	00074	$123-4-5+6+7+8-9-A^*B$	$-B+A-(-9-87)-(-6-5+43)-(-2-1)$
0063	00075	$12+3+4+5-6-7+8-(-9A)+B$	$B-(-A-98-765)+43^*-21$
0064	00076	$12-(-3-(-45+6+7-8+9A-B))$	$B+A-(-98+7-(-6+5^*-4-3-21))$
0065	00077	$1+2-(-3-(-45+6-(-7+8)))-9-A^*B$	$B+A-(-98+7+65)-(-4-3)+21$
0066	00078	$123-4-5-6+7+89-A^*B$	$B-(-A-98)-(76-5-43)-21$
0067	00079	$-12-3-4-5+6+7-8-(-9A+B)$	$-B-A+98-(-7^*6+5)-43-2^*1$
0068	00080	$-12-3-4+5-(6-7+8)+9-(-A-B)$	$-B+A+9+87-6-5+4+32+1$
0069	00081	$-1+23+4-56-78-(-9A)^*-B$	$BA-(9-(8-7)-(-6-5-4+32^*-1))$
006A	00082	$-12+3+4-(-5+6+7)+8-9+AB$	$B+A+9-(-87-(-65+43-21))$
006B	00083	$1-23-(4-5-(-6-7)+8)-(-9A-B)$	$-B-A+98+7+6^*5-(-43+2)^*-1$
0070	00084	$1+2+3+4-56-7-8-9+AB$	$-B-(-A9+87-65)-(-4+3+2-1)$
0071	00085	$-1-2-3-4-5-6+7-8+9A-B$	$B+A9-8+7+6^*-5+4-3-21$
0072	00086	$1-23+4+5+6+7+8+9-A-B$	$BA-9+8-7-6-5-4-(-3-21)$
0073	00087	$123-(45-6)+7-8-(9A+B)$	$-B-A-9+8+7-(-6-5+43^*-2)+1$
0074	00088	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8-(9-(-A-B))$	$B-A-(-98+7+6+5^*4-3)-(-2+1)$
0075	00089	$-12-3+4+5+6+7+89-AB$	$BA+9+87-65-4^*(-3+21)$
0076	00090	$1-(2-(3+4+5+6+7+8-9A+B))$	$-B+A+9-(8-76)+(-5+4)^*3+2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0077	00091	$1+2+34*(-5+6)-(78-(9+AB))$	$BA+9+8-76-(-5+4)*-3+21$
0078	00092	$-1+23-(4*5-6*7)-8-(9-A-B)$	$BA+9+8-76+5-4-3+21$
0079	00093	$-1-2+3-(-4-5-6+7+8+9-A*B)$	$BA-9-87-(-6-5*4)-(-32+1)$
007A	00094	$123-45+6+78+9-AB$	$B-(-A9-8)-76-(-54+3+21)$
007B	00095	$123-4-5-6*7-8+9+A*B$	$-B-(A-9-8*7-65+43-21)$
0080	00096	$-1+2+3+45-6-(-7-8-(9+A+B))$	$B-A-987-6+5*-4*-3*21$
0081	00097	$1-(2-3)+45-6-(78-9-AB)$	$-B+A9-(-8+76)-(-54+3*(2-1))$
0082	00098	$-1-2-3-(-45+67)-(-8+9)+AB$	$-B-(A-(9+8-7))+6-(-54-32)+1$
0083	00099	$1*-23-(-4-5-(6+7)-89)-(-A+B)$	$BA+9-(87-65)-(-4-(3-21))$
0084	00100	$123-(-4+56+7-8+9-A+B)$	$BA+9-8+7-6-(-5+43)+2*1$
0085	00101	$12+34-56+7+89-A+B$	$B+A-9+87-6+5-4*-3-21$
0086	00102	$-1-23-45+67-(-89-A+B)$	$B+A+9+8+76-54-32*-1$
0087	00103	$-1*(23+45-(67+89+A-B))$	$BA-9-8-7+6+5-4+3-21$
0088	00104	$12-3-(-4+56-7-(8+9+AB))$	$BA+9*-87-(-654+32+1)$
0089	00105	$1-(2+34-56)-(-78-9)-(A+B)$	$BA-98+7+65-4-3+2*1$
008A	00106	$-1-2+34+56-(-7-8)-(-9+A)-B$	$B+A9+8*-7-(6+5*-4+3)*-2*-1$
008B	00107	$-12+34+56-78+9A-B$	$-B-(-A+9*8+76+5*(-43-2-1))$
0090	00108	$-123+45-6-(-78-9-AB)$	$BA+9+8-76+5-4+32*1$
0091	00109	$-12-(-34+5)-(-6-78+9)-(-A+B)$	$BA+9-87+6+5+43-2+1$
0092	00110	$-12+3+45+6+78-9-A-B$	$-B-(A+9+8-76-54+3+2+1)$
0093	00111	$1-(-23-4+5-6+7+89-A*B)$	$-B+A+9-87*(-65+43+21)$
0094	00112	$12+3+45-(67+8)-(-9A-B)$	$B-A-9-8+76+5-4+32-1$
0095	00113	$123-45-(-67+89-A)+B$	$-B-(-A-98-7+6-5+4+3+2-1)$
0096	00114	$123+45-6-(78-9)-(A+B)$	$-B-(A-9-87+6-5+4-3-21)$
0097	00115	$12-(-3+4*(-5-6-7)+89-AB)$	$BA+9+8-(7+6+5)-(-43-21)$
0098	00116	$1*2-(34-5)-6-(-7-8-(9+AB))$	$BA-9-8-76+5-(-43-21)$
0099	00117	$123-(45-6+7-(8-9)-(-A+B))$	$BA-(9-87)-(-65-4-32)*-1$
009A	00118	$1*2-34-56+7-8-9A+B$	$B-A-9*-8-(7+6)-(5*(4+3)-2)+1$
009B	00119	$1-2+3-4+5-6+7+8+9+A+B$	$BA+9-8+7-(-6-(5-4))+32*-1$
00A0	00120	$1*2+3+4+5*6-7+8-9-AB$	$BA-98+7+65+4+3+2+1$
00A1	00121	$-1+23-4-5+6-7+89*(-A+B)$	$B-A-9-(-8-7)+65-4*-3+21$
00A2	00122	$-1+234-5-(67-8+9A+B)$	$-B+A9-8-7-(6-54-(-32-1))$
00A3	00123	$123-4-5-6-7+89-AB$	$-B-(-A9+8+76-54-32-1)$
00A4	00124	$1-234*5+6*(7-8)-9AB$	$-B-A+98-7+65-4-32+1$
00A5	00125	$123-4-(-5-6+7+89)-A-B$	$B+A9-8-7-6-5-4+32-1$
00A6	00126	$1-23-(-45-67-8)-9-(-A-B)$	$BA+98-7-65-(43-2-1)$
00A7	00127	$1-2-34-5-6*7+89+A*B$	$BA-98-76+54*3-2+1$
00A8	00128	$12-34+5-6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-(A+9)-(-87-6-5*4)-(3*-2-1)$
00A9	00129	$-1-2+3-4-(56-78)+9A-B$	$-B+A9-(8-7)+6-(5-4-3)*(2+1)$
00AA	00130	$-1*2*(3-(45-(-6+78))-9+A*-B))$	$BA+98+76-5-4+3*21$
00AB	00131	$1+234-5+6-78-9A+B$	$BA-(9+87-65)-(-4-3)+21$
00B0	00132	$1-(2-3)-(-4-5-6+7-8+9-AB)$	$-B+A+9-(8-(76-(-5-4*3-21)))$
00B1	00133	$123-4+5-6-7+89-AB$	$-B+A-(-9-8-(76-5)-4-(3+21))$
00B2	00134	$-12-3-(-45-6)-(7+8-9A+B)$	$-B+A9+87-6-5-43-21$
00B3	00135	$12-(-3+4+5+6-7-(89+A+B))$	$-BA-(98-(76-5))-(-43-21)$
00B4	00136	$12-(34-5+67)-(-89-AB)$	$B+A9-8+7-6+5-(-4+3+2)-1$
00B5	00137	$-1-234-5-6+7+8+9AB$	$BA-(98-(76-5)-(-43-21))$
00B6	00138	$-1+2-3-45+67-8-9+AB$	$-B+A-9-87-(-6*(5+43)+21)$
00B7	00139	$1-234-5-6+7+8+9AB$	$B+A9+8-76-(-5-43-21)$
00B8	00140	$-12+34-5-6-7-8+9+AB$	$B-A+9-8*-7-65-4*-32-1$
00B9	00141	$123-(-45+67-(8+9-A)+B)$	$BA+98-76-54+32-1$
00BA	00142	$123-4-(-56+7)-89+A+B$	$-B-(-A-98+7+6-5+4-32)+1$
00BB	00143	$123-(-4-56-(7+89*(A-B)))$	$B+A-9+8-(7-65-43+2*-1)$
0100	00144	$-1+234-5-6+7+8-9A+B$	$B+A9*8+7-654-(3-21)$
0101	00145	$-1+2-(-3+4+5)-(-6+7+8*-9-A+B)$	$B-A+98+76-54+3-(2-1)$
0102	00146	$-1*(23+4-(-56+7-(-89-AB)))$	$B+A9-(-8-76+54+3+21)$
0103	00147	$-1+2*-3-4-5+6+7+89-A-B$	$BA-98+76+5+43-21$
0104	00148	$12-34-(-56+7-8-9A+B)$	$BA+9-8+7+6*5-4-3-21$
0105	00149	$-12-3+4-(-5-(-6+7+89))+AB$	$-B+A-(-98-7-6+5-43+21)$
0106	00150	$-1-(2+34)+5+6+7*(-89+AB)$	$-BA+98+76+54-(3-21)$
0107	00151	$123-4-(-56+78)-(-9A)+B$	$-B-(A-98)-(-7-6+5-43)-2-1$
0108	00152	$-1-(2-(-3+45))-(-67-(-89+AB))$	$B-(A-98+7)+6-(-54-(-3-21))$
0109	00153	$-12-(34-56+7-8-9)+AB$	$B-(-A-98+7)-6-(5+4+32*-1)$
010A	00154	$-1*(234+567-89A-B)$	$BA-98+76-5+4+32+1$
010B	00155	$123-45+6-(7-8)-(-9-(A+B))$	$B-A9*8-7*6*(5-4)*(-3-21)$
0110	00156	$-12+3-45+6+78-9A+B$	$-B-A9-(87-6)-54+321$
0111	00157	$-1+2-(-3-(4-56))+78-(-9A-B)$	$B-(A-98-7-6+5-4-3-21)$
0112	00158	$1-23-4-5-6+7+8+9A-B$	$B-(-A-9-87-(65-43))-2+1$
0113	00159	$12-345-67+8*9-A-B$	$B+A-9*-8-7+6*-54+321$
0114	00160	$123-4-(5*6-78)-(9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-98-7-(-6+54))-(-3+2+1)$
0115	00161	$-1+2+3+4+5-6+7-8-(9-AB)$	$B+A9-87-6+5*(43-21)$
0116	00162	$-1234-(-567-(-8+9AB))$	$BA-98+76-(-5-4)+32-1$
0117	00163	$1+23-4+5+6+7-(8-9A)+B$	$B-A+9+8*7-6-543*(2+1)$
0118	00164	$-12+34-(-5+6-7+8)-(-9-AB)$	$B+A9-8*7-6+54-3+21$
0119	00165	$12-3*-4+5+6*7*(-8+9-(A-B))$	$BA+98-7-(-6+54+3)-21$
011A	00166	$1-(-234-56)+7-(89+AB)$	$-B+A-9+8+7-6-(54*-3+21)$
011B	00167	$1+23-(-45+6)-(7+8)-(-9A+B)$	$BA9-8-765+4-321$
0120	00168	$-1-234+5-6*7-8-9-AB$	$-B+A-(-9-8*-7+6*(-54+3+21))$
0121	00169	$-12+34+56-7+89-A-B$	$B-A-(-98-7)-(-65+4)-(3+21)$
0122	00170	$-1+23+4-(5-6-7)-(8-9)+AB$	$-BA-(9-8-7+65*-4)-(3-2+1)$
0123	00171	$-12-(-3-45+6+7-8+9-AB)$	$-B-(A9-(8-76))-(-54-321)$
0124	00172	$-1+2-3-45+6+7+8+9A+B$	$-B+A-(9+8+765-43*21)$
0125	00173	$1+2+3+45-67-89-AB$	$B+A-(98-7)+6*5-43*(2-1)$
0126	00174	$-12-34+5-6+7+8+9*AB$	$B+A9-8+7+6+5-4+3+21$
0127	00175	$1-2+3+4+5-6-(-7-8)-9+AB$	$B+A98-7-(654+321)$
0128	00176	$-12+34+56-(-78-(-9-A)-B)$	$-B-(A98+76-5+4*-321)$
0129	00177	$12-3*-4-5*(67-89)-(-A-B)$	$BA-9-8-7-(-65-4)+3-21$
012A	00178	$-1-2-34-5-(-6-7+8)+9A+B$	$-B-(A-9*8-76)+5-(-4-3-21)$
012B	00179	$123+4+5+6-(-7-(-8+9))+A-B$	$B-A+98+7+6*5-4*3*2+1$
0130	00180	$12+3-4-5+6+7-(8+9-A*B)$	$-B-(-A9+8+7-(65-4+3))-(-2+1)$
0131	00181	$-1-2+3-(-45-6-7-8-9A+B)$	$B-(-A+98-7-65*4-(-32-1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0132	00182	$123 - (4+5-67) - (-8^*9+AB)$	$B - (-A9+8-7 - (-6-5+43)) - 2-1)$
0133	00183	$1+23 - (45 - (-6+78)) - (9-AB)$	$BA - 9-8+7+65 - (4 - (3-21))$
0134	00184	$12+34+5+6-7+89+A+B$	$B - (-A9 - (-8+7)) - (-6 - (5-4) - 32^*1)$
0135	00185	$-1+2+3 - (-45-6)+7 - (-8 - (9A-B))$	$-B - (-A9-87) - (65-4) - (-32+1)$
0136	00186	$-1-2-3^*-4-56+7+89+AB$	$-B-A+9 - (-8+76) - 5^*-43+21$
0137	00187	$12-34+5-6+78-9+AB$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*(7-6)^*5+4^*32^*-1$
0138	00188	$12-3+4+56 - (7+8) - (9-AB)$	$-B+A9+87-6+5-4 - (3+21)$
0139	00189	$-1+2^*3-4 - (-56 - (7+8+9A)) - B$	$B-A^*(-9-8)+7+65 - (43+21)$
013A	00190	$123 - (-4+5+67 - (-8+9A-B))$	$-B - (-A-98-7-6+5^*-4^*3+2^*-1)$
013B	00191	$1-2 - (3+4+5^*6+7-89-AB)$	$B - (-A9-8) - (-76+5+4-32^*-1)$
0140	00192	$12-3+45+6+7+8+9A-B$	$-B+A9+8+7+65+4 - (-3+21)$
0141	00193	$-1+23 - (-4-56+7-89-A+B)$	$B - (-A-98+76+5+4^*-32+1)$
0142	00194	$-12+34+5+6+7+89-A-B$	$BA-9+87+6 - (5^*4+3+21)$
0143	00195	$123+4 - (5 - (-6-7+8^*-9)+A^*-B)$	$BA-9+87+6-5-4+32^*-1$
0144	00196	$-12^*(-345-678+9AB)$	$B+A-9+8+76+54-3+21$
0145	00197	$-1-23+45+67-8-9^*-A+B$	$BA+98+7 - (-6-5+4+3^*21)$
0146	00198	$12+3+4+5-6 - (-78-9)+A+B$	$-B - (-A - (98-7)+6 - (-5-43^*-2-1))$
0147	00199	$123 - (-45+6) - (-7-89) - AB$	$B+A - (-98 - (7+6) - (-5+43)) - (-2-1)$
0148	00200	$-1-2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9 - (-8^*7-6 - (5 - (-4 - (3-21))))$
0149	00201	$123+4 - (-5-6+78-9A+B)$	$B+A+9-87-6+5^*43+21$
014A	00202	$123-45+6+7-8-9^*-A-B$	$BA+9+87-6 - (5-43)^*(-2+1)$
014B	00203	$-1+23+4+56-7-8-9+AB$	$BA-9+87-6-5+4+32-1$
0150	00204	$12-34-5+6-7 - (-89-AB)$	$BA+98-76-5 - (-4-32) - 1$
0151	00205	$-1 - (-2+3 - (4-5-6) - (78-9+AB))$	$BA+98+7+6-54-3 - (-2+1)$
0152	00206	$-1-2+3-4+5+6+7+8+9A-B$	$BA9-876+5^*(43+2)^*-1$
0153	00207	$1+234+5 - (6+7)+8+9-AB$	$BA - (-9-8-76+54+3-21)$
0154	00208	$123 - (-4-56+7-89+AB)$	$BA - (98-76 - (54+3+21))$
0155	00209	$-1-2-3+4 - (5-67) - (-8-9A)+B$	$-B - (-A9-8-76+5-4+3+2+1)$
0156	00210	$1^*(-2+3-4+5)^*(67-89+AB)$	$BA+98 - (76 - (54+3-21))$
0157	00211	$-12+34-5+67-8+9+A*B$	$B+A9+87-6-54-32^*-1$
0158	00212	$-1+23 - (-45+6-7) - 8+9+AB$	$-BA-98+765 - (432+1)$
0159	00213	$-1+2^*(3 - (-4-5) - (-67-8-9)) - (-A+B))$	$B-A-9 - (-87-65)+4+32-1$
015A	00214	$-1-2+3 - (-4-5)+6 - (-78 - (9A-B))$	$BA+98+7-65+43-21$
015B	00215	$-1 - (-23-45)+6 - (7-8) - (-9A-B)$	$B - (-A9-87+65 - (43-2^*1))$
0160	00216	$-1 - (2+3)+4+5+6^*7 - (-8-9-A*B)$	$BA-9+8+7 - (-65 - (-4+3^*-2+1))$
0161	00217	$-1+23 - (45+6-7^*(8+9) - AB)$	$BA+98-76-5+43+2+1$
0162	00218	$123 - (4+5) - (6-78+9A+B)$	$B+A98-76^*5^*(-4+3-2)+1$
0163	00219	$-12 - (-3-4) - 56^*-7 - (89+AB)$	$BA+98+7 - (6+5)+4-32-1$
0164	00220	$1 - (23 - (45+67-8 - (9-AB)))$	$B-A+98+7^*(6+5)+43-21$
0165	00221	$12 - (-345-6^*-7) - (89+AB)$	$BA-9 - (-8+7)+6+5 - (-43-21)$
0166	00222	$-12 - (-345+6) - 7 - (89+AB)$	$-B+A-98-7-65^*-4-32^*-1$
0167	00223	$12 - (-34-5^*-6)+78 - (-9A+B)$	$BA+98 - (-7 - (-65-4) - (32+1))$
0168	00224	$-123+45-678+9A*B$	$BA+98 - (-7-6)+5 - (43+2-1)$
0169	00225	$1234-567+8^*(-9A-B)$	$-BA - (98-76 - (-54+321))$
016A	00226	$1+234-5-6 - (-7-8+9A-B)$	$B - (-A+98-7)+65^*4 - (-3-2-1)$
016B	00227	$123+4+56+7^*(-8+9) - (A+B)$	$B+A-9 - (-8-76) - (-5+4^*(-3-21))$
0170	00228	$-1 - (-2-3+456+7^*-89-AB)$	$B+A9+87 - (-6-5+4) - (-3+21)$
0171	00229	$1 - (-234-5) - 67+89-AB$	$B+A9+8+76-5 - (4 - (-3+2)) + 1$
0172	00230	$-1+23+4-5+6+7+8+9A-B$	$-BA+9+8+76-5^*(43+2)^*-1$
0173	00231	$12+3 - (-4-56-7-8 - (9A+B))$	$B-A9-87-6+5-4+321$
0174	00232	$1-2 - (-34-5) - (-67-8) - 9^*-A+B$	$-B-A9-8 - (7+6+54-321)$
0175	00233	$-12+3-4 - (-56-7^*(-89+AB))$	$BA-9+87-6+5-4+3-2+1$
0176	00234	$123+4+5+6-7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+87-6 - (-5-4) - (3+2^*1)$
0177	00235	$-12+3+45 - (6-78)+9A-B$	$-BA+9 - (87-654) - 321$
0178	00236	$1-23-45+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA - (9+8)+7 - (-6+5-43^*2)+1$
0179	00237	$123+45 - (6 - (-7-89+AB))$	$B+A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+21$
017A	00238	$123 - (4+56) - (-7-8) - (9-AB)$	$B-A+9-8 - (-76+5+4^*-32) - 1$
017B	00239	$1+234-5+6-7-89+A+B$	$B+A9+8-7+6+5+4+3+21$
0180	00240	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8-9+AB$	$BA-9-8-76-5^*4-3^*-2-1$
0181	00241	$-12+3+4+5^*(67-8) - (9A-B)$	$BA+9 - (8-76) - 5 - (-4-3^*(2+1))$
0182	00242	$-123 - (-456-7) - 89-AB$	$B+A9 - (-87+65)+43+21$
0183	00243	$1-23+45+6+7+8+9A+B$	$BA+9 - (-8-7-65 - (4-3)+2)+1$
0184	00244	$1+234-56+7+89-AB$	$-B - (A9-8) - 76 - (-5 - (4+321))$
0185	00245	$-123-4+5^*(-6+78) - 9A-B$	$BA+9-8+7 - (-65 - (-4-3+21))$
0186	00246	$123-45+6+7+8+9A+B$	$-B-A9 - (8-7+6) - (54-321)$
0187	00247	$-123-45-678+9AB$	$-BA+9-87+6+5^*4+321$
0188	00248	$-1-23+45 - (6 - (-7+89+AB))$	$-B+A987+6^*5^*432^*-1$
0189	00249	$12-345 - (-6+7^*-89) - A-B$	$B - (A-98)+7+6^*5^*4+3-2^*-1$
018A	00250	$1234 - (-5-67^*-8-9^*-AB)$	$B-A9 - (87-654+321)$
018B	00251	$123-4+5-6^*7-8 - (-9A-B)$	$BA+9 - (8-76-5-4^*3-2+1)$
0190	00252	$-1-2 - (34-56+7) - (-89-AB)$	$-B+A9+9-87+65^*4+32+1$
0191	00253	$123-45-6-7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A9-8+76+5+43-2-1$
0192	00254	$1 - (23-45 - (6+78+9A) - B)$	$B+A-9-87-6^*-54-32-1$
0193	00255	$-12-34+56 - (-7-89-AB)$	$BA-9^*(-8-7)+(-6-5)^*(4-3)^*2^*1$
0194	00256	$-12 - (-34+5)+6-7 - (-89-AB)$	$BA-9+8+76+54-32-1$
0195	00257	$-12+3 - (-45+6-78-9A-B)$	$-B+A9+87 - (-65+4 - (-32+1))$
0196	00258	$-12+3 - (-4 - (56+78+9A)+B)$	$B+A9+8^*7 - (-6-5) - 43^*(-2+1)$
0197	00259	$-12+34-5 - (-6-78)+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7-6+5+4^*(3+21)$
0198	00260	$12+3-4 - (56^*-7+89)+A^*-B$	$BA+98 - (76-54)+3+21$
0199	00261	$-1-2-3^*-45+67-89+AB$	$B+A^*98-7^*(65+43+2)^*1$
019A	00262	$-12+345-67-8+9-AB$	$-BA-98-7+6+5+4+321$
019B	00263	$1-234 - (5 - (-6-7+8))^*(-9+A^*-B))$	$-BA-9+87+6+5-4^*-3^*2^1$
01A0	00264	$12+34 - (-5 - (67+89+A+B))$	$-B+A9 - (8-76) - (-54+3-2)+1$
01A1	00265	$1+23+4-5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8 - (7-65 - (43+2+1))$
01A2	00266	$-12+34+5+6-7 - (-89-AB)$	$B+A9+8 - (7-65) - (-43 - (-2-1))$
01A3	00267	$-1 - (234-567) - 8^*9-AB$	$-B+A9+87+6 - (-5+4-32-1)$
01A4	00268	$1-23-4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+87-6+5+43^*-2^*1$
01A5	00269	$1-2^*(3-4^*(56+78)) - 9^*A*B$	$-B - (A9+8+76^*-5-4+32)+1$
01A6	00270	$-1 - (2+3) - (-45+678-9^*AB)$	$-B-A9+8^*-7^*6+5+43-21$
01A7	00271	$123-4+5+6+7+8-9A+B$	$BA+9+8^*7-6+5+4+3^*-2^*-1$
01A8	00272	$-1+23+45-6 - (-78-9A) - B$	$BA+98+7-6+5+4+3+2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
01A9	00273	$12-3+45+67-(-8+9-AB)$	$B-(-A-98)-(-7-65-43-2+1)$
01AA	00274	$-1+2-3+45-678+9^*AB$	$B+A9+8-7-6+5+4+3^*21$
01AB	00275	$12-345+6^*-78+9A^*B$	$-BA9+876+543-21$
01B0	00276	$123+4^*-5^*-6-(-78-(-9A+B))$	$-BA-9-87+65-4+321$
01B1	00277	$123-4-(-5-(-6+7-8)+9-AB)$	$BA+9-(-87+6+5+4-32^*1)$
01B2	00278	$-1-23-(456+7)-8^*-9A+B$	$BA+98-7+65-43+2-1$
01B3	00279	$-123-456+789-(A+B)$	$-BA-9-8+7-6-5^*4+321$
01B4	00280	$123-4+5-6-(7+8-9A)+B$	$B+A9+87-(6-5-43)-21$
01B5	00281	$-1+2+345-67-89-A-B$	$B-A9+8+7-65+4+321$
01B6	00282	$123+45-6-7-8+9^*A-B$	$B-(-A+98)-(-7+65-4-321)$
01B7	00283	$-1-2+345-6-(78-9)+A^*-B$	$BA-9+87-6-(-5-43+2+1)$
01B8	00284	$1-(-234-56)-(-7+89+A-B)$	$BA+9+87-(6-54)-3-21$
01B9	00285	$-1+234-(-56-7)-(-8+9A)+B$	$BA+98-(-7+6)-(-54+32)^*1$
01BA	00286	$-1-23+4-5+67-(-89-AB)$	$-BA-98+7-(65-432^*1)$
01BB	00287	$1+2+34-5+6+7+89+AB$	$B+A+9-8+7+6+(-5-4)^*(-3-21)$
0200	00288	$-1-(23-(-4+5))-(-67+89)-AB$	$BA+9+8-(-76-(5-4))+32^*1$
0201	00289	$1+234-(-56+7-(-8-9A+B))$	$BA+98+76-5-(43+2+1)$
0202	00290	$1-2+345-6^*-7-89-AB$	$B+A-98+7+6^*54-3-(2+1)$
0203	00291	$1+2-(3-(-4+56-7))-89-AB$	$BA+9+87+6+5-(-4+3)+21$
0204	00292	$1-234+5^*(6+78)+9A+B$	$-BA-(-987+654+32-1)$
0205	00293	$-1+234-(-56+78+9-(-A+B))$	$B-A+98+76+54-3+21$
0206	00294	$1-(-23-4+567+89^*-A-B)$	$-B-A-98-76-(-54-321)$
0207	00295	$12-(34-(-567-8^*(-9-AB)))$	$-B-A9-87+65+4+321$
0208	00296	$1+234-56+7-89+AB$	$BA+9+87+65+4-32-1$
0209	00297	$-1-(2-345+67)-(-89-A+B)$	$B+A9-(-8-76-(54-3))-2^*1$
020A	00298	$1+234+5-6-(-78-9)-AB$	$-B+A9+87+65+4-3-2+1$
020B	00299	$-12-3-4+5+67+89+AB$	$-BA9-(-876-543+2)+1$
0210	00300	$123-4-(56-78-9A+B)$	$-BA9-(-876-543^*(2-1))$
0211	00301	$-1+234-(5+6)-(-7-8-(-9-A)))-B$	$-BA+9-87-65+432^*1$
0212	00302	$-1+234-(5-67-8+9A-B)$	$-BA+9-87-(65-432)+1$
0213	00303	$123+4-(-56-78-(-9-A-B))$	$B+A+98-7-(-6-54^*3)-21$
0214	00304	$1+234+5+67+8+9^*-A-B$	$-B+A9-(-87-6^*5)+43+2^*1$
0215	00305	$123-4-5^*-6-(7-8-9A)-B$	$BA+9-8+7^*-6^*-5-43+2+1$
0216	00306	$12+3-45-678-9A^*-B$	$BA-9+87+6+54-(3-2-1)$
0217	00307	$-123-(4+567)+89A+B$	$-BA+987-654+3-21$
0218	00308	$-12+345+6^*-7+8-9A-B$	$B+A+98+7-6-5+(-4-3)^*-21$
0219	00309	$1^*2+345-67+8-9A+B$	$B-A^*-98-(76+543)-(-2-1)$
021A	00310	$-1+2-3-4-5^*-6-(78-9A)^*B$	$-BA-9-8+7+6-5+4+321$
021B	00311	$123-(45-67)-8-(-9-AB)$	$BA+98-7+6+5+43-2^*1$
0220	00312	$12+3-45+6^*7^*8-9-(-A-B)$	$B-(-A-98)-(-7+6^*-5+4^*-32^*1)$
0221	00313	$12-3+4+56+78+9+AB$	$BA-9^*87+6^*(-54+3)^*(-2-1)$
0222	00314	$-123-(-456-7^*-8+9^*A+B)$	$B-(-A9+8)-(-76-54-3-21)$
0223	00315	$-123+4-(567-89A-B)$	$BA-(-9-87-6-5^*-4+3^*-21)$
0224	00316	$12+34-567-(-89^*-A-B)$	$-B-(-A9-(8-765))-43^*-21$
0225	00317	$-1+23+4+56+78-(-9A-B)$	$BA-(9-(8+76))-(-54+3-21)$
0226	00318	$123-45+67-8-(-9A-B)$	$-BA-(9-8-7)+6-(5+4)+321$
0227	00319	$1^*(23+45-6-(-7-8+9A))^*-B$	$B+A9+87-(65+43^*(-2-1))$
0228	00320	$123+45-6+78+9-A+B$	$-B+A9-8+76+5^*(-4-(-3-21))$
0229	00321	$-1-2+34-(-5^*67-8+9+A^*B)$	$BA-(-98+7^*-6+5-4+3-21)$
022A	00322	$12-34-56^*-7-(-8-(9-AB))$	$-BA+9^*87-6-(5-4)^*321$
022B	00323	$-1+234-5-(-6+7-(-8+9)+A)+B$	$BA+98+76-54+32+1$
0230	00324	$-1-23-4+56^*7-89+A-B$	$BA-(-9-87-6-54+3-(-2+1))$
0231	00325	$123-4-(-56+7+8-9A+B)$	$-BA9+876+543+21$
0232	00326	$1-23+(-4-56+7-(-89+A))^*B$	$BA+98+7+6-5^*4+3^*21$
0233	00327	$-1-2-3^*(-4-56-7)+(-8+9-A)^*-B$	$-B-A9-8^*-76-5^*43-2^*-1$
0234	00328	$-12-34+5^*-6^*7^*-8+9A^*-B$	$-BA+987-(654+3+2^*-1)$
0235	00329	$-12+3-456+789-AB$	$B+A9-(-87+6-(54+3))+21$
0236	00330	$123-4-56-7+89+AB$	$-B-A9-8-(-7-(654-321))$
0237	00331	$1-234-56^*7-8^*(-9-AB)$	$-BA+9+87+6^*(5+43)+21$
0238	00332	$123-(4-56+7-89)-(A-B)$	$BA+98-(-7-65+4-3^*2^*-1)$
0239	00333	$-1-23-456+789+A^*-B$	$-BA+987-654+3+2-1$
023A	00334	$-1-(2+3)-456-(-789+AB)$	$-BA+987-(654-3^*2+1)$
023B	00335	$1-234-(-567+8)-(-9A+B)$	$B-(A9-8+7+6)-(-5+4-321)$
0240	00336	$-12+34-5+67-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8+76-(-5^*43+21)$
0241	00337	$1-2+34+56+78+9+AB$	$B-(A9-8)-7-(-6+5+4-321)$
0242	00338	$123-(45-6-78-(-9+AB))$	$B-A9-8-7-(-654+321)$
0243	00339	$-12-3^*-45+6^*-7-(-89-AB)$	$-B-A9+8+765-432^*1$
0244	00340	$123+45-6+78+9+A+B$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7)+6-(5+4)+321$
0245	00341	$123-(45+678-9^*AB)$	$B-A+98^*7-6-5-(4+321)$
0246	00342	$12+34+56+7+89-A^*-B$	$BA+98+7-(-6+5-(43+21))$
0247	00343	$-123+456-7+8-9A-B$	$BA9+8+7-654-321$
0248	00344	$-12-3^*(-4+5)^*-67-8+9A+B$	$-BA-(-9-8-7-6+5-4-321)$
0249	00345	$12-345+678-9-AB$	$-B-A9-(8+7^*(-6-54)+3^*(-2+1))$
024A	00346	$-1-2-345+678+9-AB$	$B-A9-(8-765+432)+1$
024B	00347	$-1+234-5-(-6-(-7-(89-AB)))$	$-B+A-9-(87+6)-(-5-4-321)$
0250	00348	$-12+345-(6+7+(-8+9))^*A^*B$	$BA+98-(7-(-6+54)-32)+1$
0251	00349	$-1+234-(5+67-(89-A)-B)$	$BA+98-7-65-(-4-3)^*21$
0252	00350	$123-4+5+67-8+9A-B$	$-BA-9-87-6-5+432+1$
0253	00351	$12-3-456+789-AB$	$-BA+987-654-(3-21)$
0254	00352	$12+34-(-56-78)-(-9-AB)$	$B+A9+87+6+54-(-32-1)$
0255	00353	$123+4-5+67+89+A-B$	$-BA-(-9-8-7-654)-321$
0256	00354	$1+234-(56-7-89)-(A+B)$	$B-A9-(-8+7)-(-6-5^*4)+321$
0257	00355	$1+2-(345-678+9-A^*-B)$	$BA+98-(-76-5+4)-(-3-2)+1$
0258	00356	$123-45+6+78-(-9-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8-7+6^*54-32+1$
0259	00357	$-1-(2+34-(5^*67-89))-A^*-B$	$-B+A+9-(87-(-6+5))-(-4-321)$
025A	00358	$-1-2-(-345-6-(7-8))-(-9A+B)$	$-BA-9-87-(6-(5+432))-1$
025B	00359	$1-(-234-5-6+7+89-AB)$	$-B-(-A-9+87)-(-6-(-5-(4-321)))$
0260	00360	$1+234-5-67+8-(-9A+B)$	$BA-(9+8)+7-(-65-4^*32)-1$
0261	00361	$-12-345-6-7^*-89+AB$	$-B+A9-87-65^*-4+32^*1$
0262	00362	$123-(-4-5-(-6+7-8))+9^*(A+B)$	$B+A98-7+65-43^*21$
0263	00363	$12-345-(-678-9+AB)$	$BA+9+87+65+4+3+21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0264	00364	$-1 \cdot (-234-56) - (7-8) - (-9-A-B)$	$BA+98+7*6+54-3+2+1$
0265	00365	$-1 \cdot 234 - (-567+89) \cdot (-A+B)$	$-BA - (-98-7+65 - (4+321))$
0266	00366	$-1 \cdot (-23+456) - (-789+AB)$	$-B - (-A+98-76+54-321)$
0267	00367	$-123+456-78+9 - (A+B)$	$-BA - (-987+654-32*1)$
0268	00368	$-1+234+5 - (-6+78+9)+AB$	$-BA+987-654+32+1$
0269	00369	$123-45*6 - (-7+8) - 9-A*B$	$-B - (-A+98)+7*65 - (43-2*-1)$
026A	00370	$-1*2*(34*5 - (-6+78) - 9-A*-B)$	$BA9-876-54-32+1$
026B	00371	$1-23+4*(56-7+8) - (-9A-B)$	$-B-A9-8-76-5-432*-1$
0270	00372	$-123+456+7 - (89-A+B)$	$-BA-9-87+6+5+432+1$
0271	00373	$-12+345+6 - (78 - (9 - (A+B)))$	$B - (A9+8)+7*6*(-5+4)+321$
0272	00374	$1+234 - (56-7-89-A+B)$	$-BA - (98-765)+4-321$
0273	00375	$-1+234-5+67+89-AB$	$B-A - (-9-8+7*(-6+5))*-43*(-2+1)$
0274	00376	$-12-345-6*78+9AB$	$B+A - (98-7-6-5+4)+321$
0275	00377	$1+234 - (5+6+78) - (-9-AB)$	$BA+98+76+5+4*(3+2+1)$
0276	00378	$123+4+5+6*(7 - (89-AB))$	$B-A9+876-543+21$
0277	00379	$12-3+45+67+89+AB$	$BA9 - (876+54+3) - 21$
0278	00380	$-123+456-7-89+A+B$	$BA+9+8-7+65-4*32-1$
0279	00381	$-1+2*3*(4+5-67+8)+9-A+B$	$-B+A9+8*76*(5-4)-321$
027A	00382	$-1-23+456-78-9-AB$	$BA - (-9-87) - (-6 - (54-3))*-2*-1$
027B	00383	$-1*(23 - (456-78)) - (-9-AB))$	$-B - (-A98+7-6*54*-3+2+1)$
0280	00384	$-1-234-567+8*-9*(-A-B)$	$BA - (98+76) - 5-4+321$
0281	00385	$12+3-4-567-8+9*AB$	$-B-A9+(8+7+6)*(54-32-1)$
0282	00386	$1+2+345+67+8-9*(A+B)$	$BA - (-98-76) - 5+4+32+1$
0283	00387	$-12 - (-345 - (-67+89)) - A*B$	$BA - (-9 - (87-6) - 54-3*21)$
0284	00388	$-123 - (4-567) - 89-AB$	$-BA-9+8-7-65+432+1$
0285	00389	$-123+456 - (78-9) - A+B$	$-BA+9-8-76+5+432+1$
0286	00390	$-1 - (-234-5) - (-67 - (-8+9)*-A) - B$	$BA+9 - (8-7) - (6+5*(-43+2))+1$
0287	00391	$-123+456 - (78+9-A-B)$	$B+A - (-9+87-6) - (-5 - (-4+321))$
0288	00392	$1*2*(-34+5 - (6+7) - (8+9+AB))$	$B-A - (9 - (8-7+6)+54)+321$
0289	00393	$-12-3 - (-456+78+9+AB)$	$B-A+9-8+7-65+4+321$
028A	00394	$1-2+345-6-78+9A-B$	$-B-A+9*8+7-65*-4 - (-3-21)$
028B	00395	$123 - (-4-5+6-78) - (-9A-B)$	$-B+A+9 - (8-7-6*54)+3 - (-2+1)$
0290	00396	$1*(-23-4-5)*(-6 - (7+8-9A-B))$	$BA+98+76+5+4+32+1$
0291	00397	$123 - (-4+5-6 - (78+9A)) + B$	$-B-A*9*(-8-7+6+5) - (-43+2+1)$
0292	00398	$12+345+6+7+8+9-AB$	$-B-A+98-76-54+321$
0293	00399	$-1-2*3-4+5+67+89+AB$	$B+A+9 - (8+7+65 - (4+321))$
0294	00400	$12+345-67 - (8-9+A+B)$	$-B-A - (98-7-65) - 4+321$
0295	00401	$-1-23-4*5-6*7 - (-8+9AB)$	$B+A+98+7*6*5+43+2+1$
0296	00402	$1+2+34*5+6+78-9+A*B$	$-B-A9+8 - (-7-6)+54+321$
0297	00403	$-1+2+3+456-7-89-AB$	$BA-98-7-65+4+321$
0298	00404	$12 - (345-6*78-9AB)$	$-BA-9*8*7 - (-65-4 - (-32-1))$
0299	00405	$-1+234-56+7+8+9A+B$	$-B-A9+8+7+65-4+321$
029A	00406	$-1-2+345 - (-6+78)+9-A+B$	$BA+98 - (-76 - (54 - (3+2)))+1$
029B	00407	$1+2+345-67+8-9A-B$	$-B-A-98+7-65-432*-1$
02A0	00408	$123+4-567-8*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A*(9-8)*(7+65-4-32)-1$
02A1	00409	$1+2+345-67 - (-8+9) - (A-B)$	$B - (A9-8+76) - (5-432)*1$
02A2	00410	$-12+3 - (-456+78) - (9A+B)$	$-B+A-98+76-5*4+321$
02A3	00411	$123 - (4+5-6-7) - (-89-AB)$	$B+A9-8 - (7-65*4 - (3-21))$
02A4	00412	$-1+234+56-7-89+AB$	$BA9-87+65-43*21$
02A5	00413	$123-4+5*(-67+8+9A)+B$	$BA9-876-54 - (-3-2)+1$
02A6	00414	$1 - (23+456) - (-78-9*A*B)$	$B-A+9+87+6-5-4*-3*21$
02A7	00415	$-1-2-3+456-78-9A-B$	$B+A - (-98-7-65*4) - (32-1)$
02A8	00416	$1-2 - (-345+6*7 - (89-AB))$	$B-A-98-7 - (65-432-1)$
02A9	00417	$-1+2+3*4*-5-6*7*-8 - (-9-AB)$	$BA-98 - (-7+65) - (-4-321)$
02AA	00418	$-12+345-67 - (89-AB)$	$-B+A-98-7*65-4 - (3-2)+1$
02AB	00419	$1 - (-2-3-4*5*6*7+8+9AB)$	$BA-98*(7-6) - 54+321$
02B0	00420	$1 - (2-3+45+678-9AB)$	$B-A9+8+(7 - (65+432))*-1$
02B1	00421	$-1 - (-234+5)+67 - (-8+9-A-B)$	$-BA-98 - (76-543)+2*-1$
02B2	00422	$-1-23 - (456-789 - (-A-B))$	$-B-A - (-987 - (-654-3-21))$
02B3	00423	$1*23+4*(-5+6)*(7+89-A+B)$	$-B - (A+9) - (8-7-6 - (-5-4) - 321)$
02B4	00424	$12+345-67 - (8+9-A-B)$	$-BA-98-76+543+2-1$
02B5	00425	$1-2+34*5-6 - (-78-9-AB)$	$-B+A98-765 - (-4+32) - 1$
02B6	00426	$-1+234-5 - (-6-7*(8+9)+A+B)$	$-BA-98-76 - (-543-2)+1$
02B7	00427	$-12-345+678-9-A-B$	$B-A9+87-6-5-4+321$
02B8	00428	$-1-2+345-6+78-9-AB$	$-B - (-A+98-7+65-432-1)$
02B9	00429	$12 - (3+45) - (678-9AB)$	$BA9-876 - (5+4*3) - 21$
02BA	00430	$12+3 - (-456-7 - (-89-AB))$	$B-A - (98-7+65-432)+1$
02BB	00431	$1 - (2-345) - (-67-8+9+AB)$	$BA9-876-5+4-32-1$
0300	00432	$-1*-23*(4+5-6-7+8-9+A+B)$	$B+A98-765-43+2-1$
0301	00433	$-12-3-456+789-A-B$	$-B+A-9 - (-8+7+6) - (5+4-321)$
0302	00434	$1 - (-2-345) - (6-78) - (9+AB)$	$B+A-98-7-65+432-1$
0303	00435	$1+2+345-67-89+AB$	$B+A-98-76+5+432+1$
0304	00436	$-1*(2-34-56*7-8*(9A-B))$	$B-A9+87*6-54-3+2+1$
0305	00437	$-12+345+678+9*A*B$	$-B+A98+7*65 - (43+21)$
0306	00438	$1+23+456-78 - (9+AB)$	$-B+A-9-87*-6-5*(4-32)*-1$
0307	00439	$-1-2+345-6+78-9A-B$	$B - (A+9+8) - (7-6 - (-5+4) - 321)$
0308	00440	$12-34-56*7-8 - (9-A)+B$	$BA - (9-8-76-5*(4+32)) - 1$
0309	00441	$12+345+67-8-9A-B$	$BA9-876+5+4-32-1$
030A	00442	$-123+456-7+8-9-A-B$	$BA9-876 - (-5-4-32*-1)$
030B	00443	$1+234+56-78+9+AB$	$B - (-A9+87) - (6*-54+3-21)$
0310	00444	$-12+34+5*(-6+78) - (-9+A+B)$	$B - (A-987+654+3+21)$
0311	00445	$1-23+456-78-9*A+B$	$BA9-876-54-32*-1$
0312	00446	$12+345-67-89+AB$	$BA+9*-8-76+5+4+321$
0313	00447	$-1+2+345 - (-6+7) - (8+9+A+B)$	$-BA+98+76-54*3*-2-1$
0314	00448	$12 - (-345 - (-6-7) - (-8-9)) - (A+B)$	$BA9-876-5+4+3-21$
0315	00449	$-1-2+3+456 - (78-9) - A*B$	$B+A98 - (765-4+32)+1$
0316	00450	$-12 - (-345+6-78+9A-B)$	$B-A+987-654+3-21$
0317	00451	$1+2+345-6+7-8*-9A*-B$	$BA+98+76+54+32+1$
0318	00452	$123+4+56+78+9-A*-B$	$-BA-9-8 - (-76-54)+321$
0319	00453	$-123 - (456-7-89A+B)$	$BA - (9-8*-7 - (-65-4+321))$
031A	00454	$-12-345-6-78*-9+AB$	$BA-98+7-6*-54 - (-32+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
031B	00455	12-345+678-9-A-B	B+A+987-654-(32-1)
0320	00456	1-(-2-(3-456)-789)-A-B	BA9-876-5-4+3*2*1
0321	00457	12-(-345-6-78)-(9+AB)	-BA-987-6*(5+4)*(-32+1)
0322	00458	-1-23+4-567+89A+B	B+A9*8+76-(5+4)*-3*-21
0323	00459	1+23+45*6-(-7-89+A)+B	-B+A98-765*(-4+3+2)-1
0324	00460	1-2-3+4-567-(-89A+B)	-B+A-9-8+7+654-321
0325	00461	-12+3-4+5-678+9AB	-B+A98-(765+4)+3*2-1
0326	00462	123+4-5+6+(78-9A)*-B	-B-A-(-9-876)-(543-2)+1
0327	00463	-1+2-3+45+6*78-9-AB	BA-98-7+6*(-5+4-3*-21)
0328	00464	1+2-345+678-9+A-B	-BA9-87-6*5*(-43-21)
0329	00465	-12+345-(-6+7-89)-A*B	-B+A+9-8-7+6+5+4+321
032A	00466	-1+234+5+6+7-8+9A+B	-B-A*-9*(8-7)-(6+54-321)
032B	00467	-12+3-4-567+89A+B	-BA-9+87-6+54+321
0330	00468	1-2-(3+45-67*8-(-9A+B))	B-A-(-987+654+3)-(2-1)
0331	00469	-123+4-567-(-8-9AB)	-B+A-9+8+7+6+5-4+321
0332	00470	12-(-3-456-(-7-8*9+A*-B))	-BA+9-8+76+54+321
0333	00471	-1-234+56-7*-89-(-A+B)	B-A-9+8+765+432*-1
0334	00472	-12+345+6-7-(-8-9-(-A+B))	-BA+98-(7+6*-54+3-2-1)
0335	00473	1*-2-(-3+4-5+678-9AB)	BA-(9-(-87+6))-(-5*-4-321)
0336	00474	-12-(-345+6+78-(-9*-A+B))	-B-A-98-(-76-54-321)
0337	00475	-123-456+7+89A+B	-B-(-A9-(-87-6)-5-4)+321
0338	00476	1+2+3+4-5-678+9AB	-B+A9-8-76-5+4+321
0339	00477	-1-2+345+67-89+A+B	-B+A+9+876+(543+2)*-1
033A	00478	-1-2+345-6+7+89-A*B	-B-(A-9-87)-6-(54-321)
033B	00479	-1+23+45*(6+7)-89-AB	-B-A9+8+76+54+321
0340	00480	1*-2+3*4*5*6+7+8+9A-B	-B-A*9*(8-7)*-6-(-5-(-43-(2+1)))
0341	00481	1234-56-78-9AB	B+A98-(765-4+3-2*-1)
0342	00482	-1-(-2-3)-(-4+567-89A-B)	-B-A9+8*(7+6+54)-3*2*-1
0343	00483	12-(3+456)+789-A+B	B-A-9+8-(-76+54)+321
0344	00484	1-234-5+678-9-AB	BA9+8-765-4*-32*-1
0345	00485	1-23-4+5-(-6*7*8-9+AB)	-BA-9-87*-6-5-4*3*-2-1
0346	00486	-1*23*(-45-67-8-9+AB)	-B+A98-(765-4)-(-3-21)
0347	00487	-12+3*45-678+9A*B	-B-(-A9+87-6)-(-5-4-321)
0348	00488	-1-(-23+4-(-5-(678-9AB)))	-BA-9+87-65+432-1
0349	00489	-12+345+6+7-89+A*B	-BA+987-(-6+543+2+1)
034A	00490	-1-2+345-67-(-8+9*-A+B)	B+A9*8+7*(-65-4-(-3+2-1))
034B	00491	1-234-5-6+78*9-A+B	B-A9+8+76*5+4*32-1
0350	00492	-1-(234-(5+678))-(-9-AB)	-BA-(-9-8+7-6-5-432+1)
0351	00493	12-345+678+9+A-B	-B-A9+876+5+432*-1
0352	00494	1+2-(-345+6)-(-789+AB)	B-A-(98-7+6+5-(432-1))
0353	00495	-1+234-(-56-78-9+A-B)	-B+A98-7*(-6-(-5-4-3))*21
0354	00496	-1-(-23-4-(-5-678))+9AB	BA9-876-(-54-(-32-1))
0355	00497	12-3+4-567+89A+B	B-A-98-7-(-6+54)+321
0356	00498	-1+2-3-45*-6-7*(89-AB)	-B-A-(9-8)-(-7-6-54-321)
0357	00499	12+345+6*-7*(-8+9+A-B)	BA9-876-5-4-(-32+1)
0358	00500	1+23-456+789-A+B	-BA-9-87-6-5*-4*32*1
0359	00501	-12+345+6*-7-8*-9*(-A+B)	B-A9-(-8-76)+54+321
035A	00502	1-234-5-(-678-9)-AB	B+A98-7*-6*5+43*-21
035B	00503	-1+23+45*(-6-(78-9A)-B)	-BA+987+6*5-4*32*-1
0360	00504	-1+234-(56-7-89)+AB	-B+A+9-(-876+543-21)
0361	00505	-12+3-4-5-67*-8-9A+B	-BA+987-6-543+21
0362	00506	-12+345-67-8-9+AB	-BA-9-8*(-76-(-5-4+3)+2)+1
0363	00507	-12-3+45-678+9AB	BA9-876+54-3-21
0364	00508	12+345-6-7-8-(-9-A)+B	-B-A9-8-76+543-21
0365	00509	-12-34+567-89-AB	B-A+98-7+6-54+321
0366	00510	-1-(234-5-678-9+AB)	-B-A9-(-8+7)*(-65+43)*-21
0367	00511	-123-(-4-567)+8-(-9A+B)	-BA-9-8*-76-5-(43+2*1)
0368	00512	12+3+4-(5*(6-7-(89-A)))-B)	B-A+98+76+5+4*3*21
0369	00513	-12+3+45-(678-9AB)	-BA-(9-8+76-543)-21
036A	00514	1+2+3+456-7-8-9-A*B	-B+A98-765+43+2+1
036B	00515	1+2-(-345+6)-(-7+89-AB)	-BA-(-9+8)-(-76-543+21)
0370	00516	1-2-(3-456)-(78+9-(-A-B))	B-(-A+98)-(-76-54-321)
0371	00517	1234-56-7*8-9AB	-BA+987+6-543+21
0372	00518	12+345+6+78+9*-A+B	-BA+9-(8+7)*(-6-5)*4+3*(-2-1)
0373	00519	-123+456-78+9+AB	BA+9-87+654-321
0374	00520	1+2+3+456-7+8-9A-B	-B+A-(-9-8)-7-(6*(-5-4)-321)
0375	00521	-1+2+345-(67+8)-9+AB	B-A+987-65+432-1
0376	00522	1-2-3+456-7-(8+9*A)-B	B+A-98-7+6+5+432-1
0377	00523	-1-2-(-345-67)-8-9-(A+B)	BA9+876+54*-32*1
0378	00524	12+345-(67-89-A+B)	B-(-A98+765)-(-4-32*1)
0379	00525	1+234-5*(-6-7)+(-8+9)*AB	-B+A-9-8+7-65-(-432+1)
037A	00526	12-(-345+67-(89-A+B))	BA-(-9-(-8+7)+65)-4+321
037B	00527	-1+234-56-7*(-8-9-(A+B))	-BA-(-9+87)-(-6-543)+2*-1
0380	00528	-1*2*-3*(-4+5)*(6+7+8-9A-B)	-BA+98*(7-6+5)-43+21
0381	00529	-1-2+3*-45-6-(-78*9+AB)	B-(A+9+87*-6+5-(-43-21))
0382	00530	-1+2*3*-45-(-678-(-9A+B))	-BA+98+76+5-(-4-321)
0383	00531	-1-2+3+45-6*(7-89)-A*B	-BA+9+8-76+543-21
0384	00532	1-2+345-67+8+9A*B	B+A98-765+43-2+1
0385	00533	1+23+456-7-8-(-9+AB)	BA-(9-(8-7))-(-6-54+321))
0386	00534	-123+4+5-6-7-8*9*-A-B	-B-(A+9-8)+76+5+4+321
0387	00535	-12+34*(-56+78-9)-AB	B+A98-765-(-43+2*-1)
0388	00536	-1*(2-345-67-89+AB)	-BA-9-87-(-6-543-21)
0389	00537	1-2+345-67-8-(-9-AB)	-B+A+9-(8-7)-(-65+4-321)
038A	00538	1234-(5-6)-78-9AB	-B-A*-98-76-54-321
038B	00539	-1+2+345-(67+8-9-AB)	BA9-87*-6-54*(3+21)
0390	00540	12+3+456+7-89-A-B	BA9-(876-54)+3-2*-1
0391	00541	12+345-6-78+9+AB	-B-A-9+8+7*65-4*3*2*-1
0392	00542	-1+234+5+67*(-8+9)+AB	BA9-876-5+43+21
0393	00543	-1+2*-345+67+8+9AB	B+A+9-87+6-5+432+1
0394	00544	1-2+3+4-56+7*89-AB	BA9-8-765-43-21
0395	00545	-1-(-2-(-34+567))-89+A*-B	-B-(-A+9-87)-6-(-5+4-321)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0396	00546	$1 - (-2 - 345 - (-67 + 8 + 9A + B))$	$-B - (-A - 98 + 76 - 54) + 321$
0397	00547	$1 + 2 - (-345 - 67 + 8 - (9 - A) + B)$	$-B - A - 98 - 76 + 543 + 2 + 1$
0398	00548	$1234 + 5 + 6 - (78 + 9AB)$	$-BA - 9 - 87 + 6 + 543 + 21$
0399	00549	$-1 + 234 - 5 - (-6 - 78) + 9A + B$	$BA - (98 + 7 - 65 + 4 - 321)$
039A	00550	$1 + 234 + 5 + 67 - (-8 - 9A) + B$	$-B - A + 9 + 87 * 65 - 4321$
039B	00551	$-123 + 456 + 78 + 9 - A - B$	$-B - A + 9 - 8 - 7 + 65 + 432 - 1$
03A0	00552	$12 + 345 + 67 + 89 - AB$	$B + A + 9 - (8 + 7 + 65 + 432 * -1)$
03A1	00553	$1234 - 5 - 67 + 8 - 9AB$	$BA + 9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 54 - 321)$
03A2	00554	$-12 - (-345 - (6 - 7) - (89 - A) + B)$	$BA - 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 * 54 - 32 * -1$
03A3	00555	$1 * -234 - (-567 - 89) - (A + B)$	$-B - A - 9 + 87 - (-6 + 5 - 4 - 321)$
03A4	00556	$1 - (-2 - (345 - 6 * -7 - (89 - AB)))$	$BA - (98 + 7 + 65) - 432 * -1$
03A5	00557	$-1 + 2 - (34 - 567 - 8 * -9 + AB)$	$BA - 9 - 87 + 6 + 54 + 321$
03A6	00558	$-123 + 456 + 7 - 8 * (-9 - (-A + B))$	$B + A + 98 - 765 + 43 + 21$
03A7	00559	$12 + 34 - 5 - 67 * -8 + 9 - AB$	$-B - A - 9 - 87 + 6 + 543 + 21$
03A8	00560	$1 - 2 + 34 * -5 - 6 * -78 + (-9 - A) * -B$	$BA9 - (-8 + 765) - (43 + 21)$
03A9	00561	$-12 - 34 + 5 * (6 - (78 - (-9 - A) * -B))$	$BA + 98 - (76 + 54) + 321$
03AA	00562	$1 - 23 - 45 + 6 + 7 * 8 * 9 + AB$	$-BA - (9 + 8 * -76) - (5 + 4) - (-3 + 2) + 1$
03AB	00563	$1 + 23 + 456 - (-7 - 8) + 9 - AB$	$-BA - 9 + 8 - 76 - (-543 - 21)$
03B0	00564	$-12 - 345 + 678 + 9A - B$	$-B - (-A - 9 - (876 - 543)) - 21$
03B1	00565	$-12 + 345 - (6 - 78 - 9) + A - B$	$B - A - 98 - 76 + 543 - 2 + 1$
03B2	00566	$12 + 3 * -4 * 5 - 6 * (-78 - 9 - (-A + B))$	$B - (A + 9 - 87) - (-654 + 321)$
03B3	00567	$-1 - (-234 + 567) + 89 * A - B$	$B - A - 98 - 76 + 543 + 2 - 1$
03B4	00568	$1 - 2 * 3 * 45 + 6 + 7 + 89 + AB$	$BA - 9 - (87 + 65 - 432 - 1)$
03B5	00569	$-12 + 345 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 9A - B$	$B + A - (-9 + 8 + 76 * (-5 + 4) - 321)$
03B6	00570	$-123 + 456 - 7 + 89 - A + B$	$-BA + 98 - 7 - 6 - (5 - 432) * 1$
03B7	00571	$-123 - (-456 - 78) - (-9 - A + B)$	$BA9 - (8 + 765 + 43 - 2 * 1)$
03B8	00572	$-1 + 2 + 345 - (-6 - (78 + 9)) - A - B$	$BA9 - 876 + 54 + 32 - 1$
03B9	00573	$1 - (-2 - (3 + 4) - (567 - 89) + AB)$	$-B + A + 98 - 7 - (654 + 32 - 1)$
03BA	00574	$-1 - (234 - 567) - (-89 - (A - B))$	$-B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + 654 - 321$
03BB	00575	$-123 + 456 - (-78 + 9 - A - B)$	$-B + A - (9 - 8 + 7) - 6 * 5 - 432 * -1$
0400	00576	$-1 - (234 - 567 - 89) - (A - B)$	$B + A + 98 * 7 + 6 * 54 - 3 - 2 + 1$
0401	00577	$-1 - 23 + 456 + 78 - 9A - B$	$-B - (A - 9 - 87 + 6) - (-5 - 432) + 1$
0402	00578	$12 + 3 + 4 - 5 * (-67 - 8) - 9 + AB$	$-B + A + 9 + 87 * 6 + 5 * -4 - 3 - 21$
0403	00579	$-12 + 345 - (-6 + 7) - (-8 - 9 * A - B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 765 - 4 - 32 + 1$
0404	00580	$12 + 345 + 67 - (8 - (9 - A) - B)$	$BA - 9 - 8 - (7 - 6 + 5 - (4 + 321))$
0405	00581	$12 - (34 - 5) - (67 * -8 + 9 - (-A - B))$	$-BA + 98 - (7 - 6) - (5 - (432 - 1))$
0406	00582	$-1 * (-2 + 34 + 567 + 8 - 9AB)$	$-B + A - (98 - 7 - 65 - (432 + 1))$
0407	00583	$1 + 2 + 345 + 67 - (-8 - (9 - (-A + B)))$	$-B - A - 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 432 + 1$
0408	00584	$123 + 456 + 7 - 89 - AB$	$BA + 9 - 87 - (65 - 432 + 1)$
0409	00585	$1 + 2 - 3 + 4 * -5 - 6 - 7 + 8 * (9A - B)$	$-B + A - (-98 - 765 + 432 + 1)$
040A	00586	$12 - (-3 + 45) - (67 * -8 + 9) - (-A + B)$	$B + A + 9 + 876 - 543 - 21$
040B	00587	$1 - 234 + 567 + 8 + 9A - B$	$-BA + 9 + (87 + 65) * 4 - 3 + 2 + 1$
0410	00588	$1 - 234 - (-56 - 78 * 9 - A - B)$	$B + A - (-87 - 65 * 4) - (-32 + 1)$
0411	00589	$12 + 345 + 6 * (-78 + 9A - B)$	$B - (-A + 9 + 8 * 7 + 6 - (-5 * 43 * 2 + 1))$
0412	00590	$-1 - (2 - 3 * 4 - 5 * -6 - 7 - 8 * (-9 + AB))$	$-B - (-A - 9 - 876 + 543) + 2 - 1$
0413	00591	$-1 + 2 + 345 + 67 - 89 + AB$	$BA + 987 - 654 + 3 - 21$
0414	00592	$-12 - 34 + 5 * -6 * 7 - 8 * (-9A + B)$	$-B + A + 9 + 876 - 543 + 2 + 1$
0415	00593	$-1 - (2 - (345 - 6)) - (-7 * (-8 + 9) - A * B)$	$-B + A * (-9 - 8) - (-7 + 6 - 543) - 2 * -1$
0416	00594	$-12 - (-3 - (456 + 78)) - (9A + B)$	$BA9 + 8 - (765 + 4 + 32 * 1)$
0417	00595	$1 + 23 - (-4 - (567 - 89) + AB)$	$B - A + 98 + 7 - (-654 + 321)$
0418	00596	$1 + 2 - (345 - 678 - (-9 + AB))$	$-B - (A + 98 + 7) - (-6 - 543) - 21$
0419	00597	$12 - (-3 - 4 * 5) - (6 * 78 - (9 + A - B))$	$-B + A + 9 + 8 + 765 + 432 * -1$
041A	00598	$1 - 23 - 456 + 7 - (-89A + B)$	$-BA + 98 + 765 - 4 - 321$
041B	00599	$12 + 345 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9A - B$	$-B - A - 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 543 - 21$
0420	00600	$-1 + 2 - 3 - 456 + 789 + AB$	$-BA - (98 - 76) - (-543 + 2 + 1)$
0421	00601	$1 + 2 - (-345 + 6 + 7) - (-89 - A - B)$	$BA + 9 - 87 * -6 + (5 + 43) * (-2 - 1)$
0422	00602	$-123 - (4 - 567 - (8 - 9 - A - B))$	$B + A - 9 + 876 - 432 - 1$
0423	00603	$-123 - 45 + 678 - (9A + B)$	$BA - 9 - (-876 + 543) - (-2 - 1)$
0424	00604	$12 + 345 + 67 - 89 + AB$	$-BA + 98 - 7 * 6 * (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
0425	00605	$12 - 3 + 456 + 78 - (9A + B)$	$BA - 98 + 76 - 5 + 432 + 1$
0426	00606	$-123 - (-4 - 567) + 89 - AB$	$-B + A - (9 - (-8 + 765)) - (4 + 321)$
0427	00607	$1 - 2 - (345 - 6 + 78) + 9 * AB$	$-B - (A - 9 - 8 - 76 - 54) + 321$
0428	00608	$1 - (-23 - 456) - (78 - 9 - A - B)$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 543 - 21$
0429	00609	$1 - 23 + 45 + 6 * 78 + 9 + A + B$	$-B - (-A - 9 + 8 + 76 - 54 + 321))$
042A	00610	$1 - 234 - 56 + 789 + A * -B$	$-B - A - 9 - 8 - (7 - 65 * 4 - 321)$
042B	00611	$-1 - (2 + 34 + 5 + 6 * -78) - (-9A + B)$	$B - A + 9 - 8 - (7 - 6) - (5 - 432 - 1)$
0430	00612	$-123 + 4 + 567 - 8 + 9 - A - B$	$-BA - (9 + 8 + 7) + 6 - (-543 - 2 + 1)$
0431	00613	$1 + 2 - 3 + 456 - 7 + 8 - 9 - A - B$	$B - A - 98 + 7 * -6 + 543 - (2 - 1)$
0432	00614	$12 - 345 - (-678 - 9A - B)$	$B - (A + 9 - (876 - 5 - 432 - 1))$
0433	00615	$12 - 345 - 6 + 789 - A - B$	$-B + A - 9 + 8 - 7 - (-6 - 5) + 432 - 1$
0434	00616	$-1 + 2 + 3 - (-456 - (78 + 9 - AB))$	$BA + 987 - 65 * -4 * -3 - 2 + 1$
0435	00617	$1 * 2 + 3 + 456 + 78 + 9 - AB$	$-BA + 98 - 7 + (65 - 43) * 21$
0436	00618	$-1 - 234 + 567 + 8 + 9 + AB$	$BA + 987 - 654 + 3 - 2 * -1$
0437	00619	$-12 - 345 + 6 + 789 + A - B$	$BA - (-9 - 876) - (543 + 2 + 1)$
0438	00620	$1 - 2 - (-345 - (6 - 7 + 8) - 9A - B)$	$-B - A + 9 + 876 + 5 - 432 - 1$
0439	00621	$-1 - 2 - (-34 - (567 - 89)) - A * B$	$-B - (A + 9 + 8) - 7 - (-6 - (543 - 2) - 1)$
043A	00622	$-1 - 23 - 45 - (-6 - 78 * 9) - AB$	$BA - (98 + 7 + 6 + (-5 + 432) * -1)$
043B	00623	$-12 - 3 + 4 - (567 - 8 - 9AB)$	$B - A - 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 543 + 2 * -1$
0440	00624	$1 * 2 * (-34 + 56) * (7 - 8) * (9 - (A + B))$	$-BA + 98 + 7 - 654 - (-3 + 21)$
0441	00625	$12 - 345 + 678 + 9 + AB$	$-BA - (9 - 876) - (5 + 4 + 321)$
0442	00626	$-1 + 23 + 45 + 67 * -8 + 9 * AB$	$BA + 98 - 76 + 5 - 4 + 321$
0443	00627	$123 - 45 + 6 + 7 * -8 * -9 + A - B$	$BA + 98 - 7 - 65 - 4 + 321$
0444	00628	$12 + 3 + 456 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A * -B$	$BA9 + 8 - 765 - (4 + 3) - (2 - 1)$
0445	00629	$-12 - 3 - 456 + 7 + 89A + B$	$-B + A - 9 - (87 + 6 - 5 - 432 - 1)$
0446	00630	$1 - (-23 + 456 - 789 - AB)$	$-B + A - 9 - (-8 * 7 + (6 + 54 + 3 - 2 + 1))$
0447	00631	$-123 - 45 + 678 + 9 - A * B$	$-B + A - 9 + 87 + 65 + 4 + 321$
0448	00632	$-1 - 2 - (-3 + 4) - (567 - (8 + 9AB))$	$B - (A - (98 + 7 + 6) - (-543 - 2 - 1))$
0449	00633	$-123 + 45 + 67 * 8 + 9 - A * -B$	$-B - (-A + 9 + 87 * -6 - (54 - 32 - 1))$
044A	00634	$-1 - (234 + 5 - 678) - (9 - A) + B$	$B - (A - 9 + 8) - (-765 - 4 + 321)$
044B	00635	$-12 + 3 - 456 + 7 + 89A + B$	$-BA - 9 - (-876 - 5 + 4) - 321$
0450	00636	$-1 + 2 + 3 - 4 - 567 + 8 + 9AB$	$B - (-A - 9 - 876) - 543 + 21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0451	00637	$12+3-4-5+6*(78-9)+AB$	$-B+A+9+8*(7+65)-4-32-1$
0452	00638	$-1+2+345+67-8*-9-A+B$	$-B+A-98-7-6+543-2-1$
0453	00639	$12-3+4-5-6+7*8*9+AB$	$-BA-98+7-(-654+32*1)$
0454	00640	$-1+23-45-(6*7-8*9*A)-B$	$-B-(-A9-(-8-76+5))+432+1$
0455	00641	$1-2-3*(-45-(6+7+8))-(-9+AB))$	$B-A-98-7*-6*(-5-4)*(-3+2-1)$
0456	00642	$1-(-234-56)-(-7-8*(9+A+B))$	$-BA-9+87+65+432-1$
0457	00643	$12-(3-456)-7-(8*(9-A)+B)$	$BA9-87-654-(32+1)$
0458	00644	$-123-4+567+8-9+A+B$	$-B+A9-(8-(7+6)-54)+321$
0459	00645	$-1+2-34-(-567+8-(-9A+B))$	$-B-A-9-(8+7-65-432+1)$
045A	00646	$-12-(-34+567-(-8+9AB))$	$-B-(A9-876)-(-5+4)-321$
045B	00647	$123+45-6*-78-9A-B$	$-B+A98-7-654+32-1$
0460	00648	$-12+345+6+78+9*A-B$	$BA-987+65-4*-321$
0461	00649	$1+234-(-5-67-89-AB)$	$B*(A9-8-76-5-4+32-1)$
0462	00650	$-123+4+567-(-8-9+A-B)$	$B-(-A9+8+76-(-5+432-1))$
0463	00651	$-123+4*(56+7+89)+A*B$	$-B-(A-98)-(-76-(5+4+321))$
0464	00652	$1+23+4-567-8+9AB$	$B+A-(-987-6+543+2+1)$
0465	00653	$1-(2+34-567-89*(A-B))$	$B+A-(-9-876+5+432*1)$
0466	00654	$-1-2*-3*4-(56-78*9)-AB$	$-B-A9+87+65+432*1$
0467	00655	$-1+23+456+7-8+9-A-B$	$-BA9+8+765-43*-21$
0468	00656	$-1+2-3-4+567-8-(9A+B)$	$-B+A9-8+76-5-(-4-321)$
0469	00657	$-12-34*-5-(678-9AB)$	$-B+A9+8-7+65+4+321$
046A	00658	$-12-(3-456-7)-(-89-AB)$	$-BA+98-(76-543-2)+1$
046B	00659	$-1+2+3+456-7+8-(9-(A+B))$	$-BA-(98+7)-(-654+3+2-1)$
0470	00660	$1+23-4-567+8+9AB$	$B+A98-7-(654-3)+21$
0471	00661	$-12+3*4*56-7*(-8+9)-A*B$	$-BA-(-9-876)-(-5-4+321)$
0472	00662	$-1-23+456-(78-9-AB)$	$B-A+98+7+65+4+321$
0473	00663	$123-456+789+A+B$	$-B+A*-98+7-6+5+4*321$
0474	00664	$-123+456+78-9*-A+B$	$BA-9+8-(7-65+4-321)$
0475	00665	$-1-23-456-78+9AB$	$B-(A-98)-(-76-5+4-321)$
0476	00666	$-123+4*-5-6+7+8*(9A-B)$	$B-A9+876-5-(-4+321)$
0477	00667	$-1+23-456-7-8+9A*B$	$-BA-98-(7-654-(3+2-1))$
0478	00668	$12+3+456+7-(8-9)-A+B$	$BA-987-65*(-4+3)*21$
0479	00669	$-12+3-4+567-8-9A+B$	$BA9+8-765-4-(-32+1)$
047A	00670	$1*2-3+4+567+8-9-AB$	$B+A-9+87-(-6+5+4)*(-32+1)$
047B	00671	$1*(-2+3)*4+567+8-9-AB$	$-B+A9+87-6-5+4+321$
0480	00672	$1-(-23-456-7-89)-A*B$	$-B+A-9*8-7+6+5+43-21$
0481	00673	$123-(-4+5+6*7-8-(-9A-B))$	$BA9-8-765+43-2*-1$
0482	00674	$12+34-567-(8-9AB)$	$B+A-9-8-76-5*4*-32*1$
0483	00675	$1-2-(3-456-(-78+9A))+B$	$B-(-A98-7+65*-4*-3-21)$
0484	00676	$1*-2+3+456+7-89+AB$	$-B+A+9-8*(-7-65+4)+3+21$
0485	00677	$-1-(-2-34)-(-5-6+7*-89-A*-B)$	$B+A9-(-8+76)-(-5+432*-1)$
0486	00678	$1-(2-345+6*7)-(-89-AB)$	$BA-9+8+7+65-4+321$
0487	00679	$-1-(2-3-456+78-9A-B)$	$BA9-(-8+765-4-32)+1$
0488	00680	$-12-3+4-(-567-(-89+A))-B$	$-BA-(-98+76-543-21)$
0489	00681	$-12-345-67+89A-B$	$B+A98-76-543-21$
048A	00682	$1234-(5+67-8)+9A*-B$	$-B-A*(-9+8)*(7-(-6+5))-(-432+1)$
048B	00683	$-1+2-3*-4*(56-7)+89-AB$	$-B-(-A98+76-(-543+2+1))$
0490	00684	$123*(-4-5-6-7-(89-AB))$	$-BA+98+76-(-5-432-1)$
0491	00685	$123+456-(7-8)-(9A+B)$	$BA-9*-87-(-65+4+321)$
0492	00686	$-12+345-(6-78-9A-B)$	$-BA+9-(87-654-(-3-2))-1$
0493	00687	$-1-(2-(3+456)-(-7-8*9+A*B))$	$BA9-(87+654-(3-2*-1))$
0494	00688	$12+3+4+567+8-(9+AB)$	$B+A-98-(7+6-(543+21))$
0495	00689	$-1-2+3+4+567+8+9-AB$	$-B+A9-8-7+(6+5)*43+21$
0496	00690	$-1-2-(-3-(456-78+9+AB))$	$BA9+8-765-(-43-(2+1))$
0497	00691	$-12-(-3-4+56*-7-89-AB)$	$-BA-98-7+654-(-3-21)$
0498	00692	$12+345-(-67+8+9-AB)$	$-BA+9-87+654+3-2-1$
0499	00693	$-12+34+567+8-(9+AB)$	$-B*(-A-(98-76+54-32+1))$
049A	00694	$-12-(3+4-567)-(-89-A)+B$	$BA-(-9-8-7*65+4+3-(2+1))$
049B	00695	$123+45-678+9AB$	$-B+A+98-7*-65-(-4-32+1)$
04A0	00696	$-1+2-(-345-67)-(-8+9)*-AB$	$-B-A-98*-7+6-(54+32)+1$
04A1	00697	$-12-(34-5*-6)+7*(-8+9A)+B$	$B+A9+87-(-6+5)-(-4-321)$
04A2	00698	$-12-(-34-567)-(-8+9)-A*B$	$BA-9+87+6-5+4+321$
04A3	00699	$12+345+67-8+9A+B$	$B+A-9+87*6-(-54-3+2*-1)$
04A4	00700	$1-(-2-(3+45+6))-(-7*8*9+AB))$	$B-(-A9+8*76)-(-5-43*21)$
04A5	00701	$1234-(-5+67)-89A-B$	$-BA-9-8+7+654-3*21$
04A6	00702	$123-45*6+78*9+A+B$	$B-A9-87-(-654+3*2-1)$
04A7	00703	$12+3+4*5-6*(-7-(89+A)+B)$	$B+A-9-8-(-7-65-432-1)$
04A8	00704	$-1-(2-34-567)+8-(9+AB)$	$BA+9+8+7+65+4+321$
04A9	00705	$12+34-(-567+8+9)-AB$	$-B+A9-87+65+432-1$
04AA	00706	$-1-(234-567)-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A+987-(65+432)-1$
04AB	00707	$12+345-(6-78)-9+AB$	$BA-9+87-6-5*-4+321$
04B0	00708	$-1+2-(-34-567-8+9+AB)$	$-B+A+987-65-(432-1)$
04B1	00709	$1-(-23+4-567-(8+9)+AB)$	$B-(-A98+76)-(-543-(2+1))$
04B2	00710	$12-(-3+456)-(-78-9AB)$	$B+A-9-8-76+543+21$
04B3	00711	$-12-(-3-456+7-8-9*A+B)$	$-B-A98+76*5+4*321$
04B4	00712	$1*(2-3+4-5-67-8)*(-9-A+B)$	$-B+A+9*-8+765-4*-3*-21$
04B5	00713	$1234-5-67-89A+B$	$-BA9-8+7-(6+54*-32-1)$
04B6	00714	$-123+456+7+89+AB$	$-BA-98+7+654+32-1$
04B7	00715	$-1*(-23+45-6+7*-89*(-A+B))$	$-B*(-A+9)*(-8+76)*(5+4+3-(-2+1))$
04B8	00716	$1-2-345-(67-89A-B)$	$-BA-98+7+654+32+1$
04B9	00717	$-1-(234+56-789-A+B)$	$-B-A9+8*-7*-6-(-54-321)$
04BA	00718	$-12-(345+6-789)-A*-B$	$-B+A*9+87-65+432-1$
04BB	00719	$12-(-345-6-78)-(9-AB)$	$B+A-(9-87-(-6-5+432+1))$
0500	00720	$1234+5-6+78-9AB$	$BA9-87+(654-32)*-1$
0501	00721	$-12+34+567-89-(A-B)$	$-B-A-98+76+543-2-1$
0502	00722	$1-2-3+4*-5-6*78+9A*B$	$BA-9-87+65-(-432-1)$
0503	00723	$-123-4+567-8+9A-B$	$-BA-9-8-7-(-654+32+1)$
0504	00724	$1-2-3-(-456+7)-(-8+9*-A)+B$	$-B-(A9+87-654-32)+1$
0505	00725	$1+2-(-3-456-(-7+89-A-B))$	$B-A9-8+76-5*4*-32+1$
0506	00726	$1-2-345+6-78-9A*-B$	$BA+98-(-7*(6-5)-4-321)$
0507	00727	$-1-(23-(456-(-7-89)-(A-B)))$	$BA+98+7+6-5+4+321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0508	00728	$1-234-5^*-6^*-7-(-89-A)^*B$	$B+A-(9-8)-(-76-5)-(-432+1)$
0509	00729	$-1-(2+345+6-789-A^*B)$	$B+A9-(87-65)+432+1$
050A	00730	$12-3-(45-67^*8)+9+AB$	$-BA-(-98+7+6)-(-543+2^*1)$
050B	00731	$1-234-5+678+9A-B$	$B-A9-(-876-54+321)$
0510	00732	$1234+5-(-6-78)-9AB$	$-B-A9+8-(-76-543)-(-2-1)$
0511	00733	$123+456-78-9+A+B$	$-BA+98-(-7-(6+543))-21$
0512	00734	$-1-2+3+4^*-5^*-6^*7-89+A-B$	$-B-(A9+8+7)+654-(32+1)$
0513	00735	$1-23+456-7+89+A+B$	$B-A9-(87-654-3-21)$
0514	00736	$1+2-3-4+567+8^*9-AB$	$-B+A98-7-6-543-21$
0515	00737	$1+2+345-(-6-7-(89+AB))$	$-BA+9+8-(-76-543)-(-2+1)$
0516	00738	$12+34+567-8-9A+B$	$B-A9+87-6+5^*4^*32-1$
0517	00739	$-123+45-6+7+8^*(9A-B)$	$B-(A9-8)-(-76+5^*4^*-32+1)$
0518	00740	$1+2^*3^*-45+678-9-A^*-B$	$B-(-A9+8+7-6+5)+432^*1$
0519	00741	$-1+2^*(345+6^*(7-(-89+AB)))$	$BA+98+76-(54-321)$
051A	00742	$1+2-(3^*-4^*(56+7)-(-8-9A-B))$	$BA9-8-7-654-3-21$
051B	00743	$-1-(-2-3-4+5)-(-6+7^*-89-(A-B))$	$B-(-A9+8)-(-76-54-321)$
0520	00744	$-123-45+678-9+A+B$	$B+A+9+8-76+543+21$
0521	00745	$1-23+4-5-(67^*-8-9)+AB$	$-B-A-(98+7)+654-(32+1)$
0522	00746	$1-234-5-(-678+9)+AB$	$-BA+98+76^*(5+4)-32^*1$
0523	00747	$1+23+4+567-89+A+B$	$-B-A9-87-6^*-5^*(-4+32-1)$
0524	00748	$-1-2+3-(456-78+9A^*-B)$	$B-A+98+7-(-6-5)+432-1$
0525	00749	$123-(-4+5^*6-7^*89+AB)$	$-BA+9^*87+6-5-4^*3-21$
0526	00750	$123+456-7^*-8-(9+A^*B)$	$B-A9+8+7+654-3^*21$
0527	00751	$12-34-(-567-8)-9-(A+B)$	$BA-(-987-6+543+21)$
0528	00752	$1+2+3-(-4-5-6^*(78+9)-AB)$	$B-A9+87-6-(543+2)^*-1$
0529	00753	$-1-23+4+567-(-8+9-(-A-B))$	$B+A-98-76^*(-5-4)-32^*-1$
052A	00754	$1^*2+3+456-7-8-9+AB$	$BA+9+8-7-6-(5-432)-1$
052B	00755	$1+2-(-3-(-4+5))^*6+7^*(89-(-A+B))$	$B+A9+8-7-(-6-5)+432+1$
0530	00756	$12+3+456-7+89+A-B$	$B-A-(-987-6^*-5+432^*1)$
0531	00757	$-12-3-45+678-9A-B$	$-BA+A98+7^*-6-543+21$
0532	00758	$12+3^*4^*(5+6-(7^*8-9A)-B)$	$B+A9+8-(7+654+3+21)$
0533	00759	$-12-(345-(6-7+89A)+B)$	$-BA9-87^*(-6+5)^*(-4+3+21)$
0534	00760	$12+34+567+8+9-A^*B$	$B-A9-8+76+543+21$
0535	00761	$-1+2-34+5-67^*8+9AB$	$B-(-A-(98+765-4)+321)$
0536	00762	$-12-3+456+7+8-(9-AB)$	$B-A^*(9+8)-7+654+3-2-1$
0537	00763	$-1-23+45^*6^*7-8-9AB$	$B+A9-87^*-6+5-4+3+2-1$
0538	00764	$-123-(45-6-789+AB)$	$B+A9+876-5-432+1$
0539	00765	$123+456-(-78+9)-AB$	$BA+987-6-(543-(2-1))$
053A	00766	$-1-2+34-5+6-7^*(-89-(A-B))$	$-BA-9^*-8+76+543-21$
053B	00767	$-12-34-(-5-(678-9))-AB$	$-B+A9-87-(-6-543+21)$
0540	00768	$-1-2-34-5+678-9-AB$	$-BA-9-8-7+654+3+2+1$
0541	00769	$-123-(-4-567)-(-8-9A-B)$	$-BA+98-7+6+543+21$
0542	00770	$-1-2-345-(-6+7-89A+B)$	$-B+A98-7-(-6+543+2+1)$
0543	00771	$1-(2-(3-4+567+89-AB))$	$BA-98-7+6+543-21$
0544	00772	$-123+4-5-(-678-9+A+B)$	$B-A9+8-(7-654)-(-32+1)$
0545	00773	$123-456+789+AB$	$-B-(-A+9)-(-8-(7-6+543+2+1))$
0546	00774	$-12-3-(4-(567+8)-9)-(A+B)$	$-B-A9-(-8-7)-(65^*4^*3+21)$
0547	00775	$-1-2+3+456+7+89+A+B$	$-B-A+98-76-(-543+2)+1$
0548	00776	$-123-4+5+678-9-(-A+B)$	$B-(A+9)+876-5-(-4+321)$
0549	00777	$12+345-6^*-7+89+AB$	$-B-A+98-76-(-543-2+1)$
054A	00778	$12-34-(-567+89-A^*B)$	$-BA-9+8-7+654+3-2-1$
054B	00779	$-12-3-45+678-9A+B$	$-B+A-9-8-(-7+6)+543+21$
0550	00780	$-1^*(2+34+5-678+9A+B)$	$BA+98-(-7+6-54)+321$
0551	00781	$-12-34+5+6-7+89A+B$	$-BA-9^*87-(654-3)^*2^*-1$
0552	00782	$12+3+4-(56-78^*9-(A-B))$	$B-A9-(87-654)+3^*21$
0553	00783	$123+456+78+9-AB$	$B-A9+8-7+654-3-21$
0554	00784	$-1-(2+34+56+7^*(-8-9A)-B)$	$-B-(-A98-7-6+543+2+1)$
0555	00785	$-1-2-(-3-4-567)-8-(9-A+B)$	$-BA-98+765-4-32^*1$
0556	00786	$-123-(4+5-678-9A-B)$	$-BA+987-654+321$
0557	00787	$123-(4-(-567-8)-9AB)$	$B-A9-8+7-(-654-3+21)$
0558	00788	$1-2+3+4-5-(-6+7^*(8-9A)-B)$	$B+A9-(8+76-543)-21$
0559	00789	$12-(345+6-7-89A+B)$	$B-(-A9+87-6)-(-543+21)$
055A	00790	$-123-(-4+56^*7)-(-8-9AB)$	$BA+9+87-(-65-(432-1))$
055B	00791	$-1+2-(3+4-567-(8-9))+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8+7+65+432^*1$
0560	00792	$-12-345-(6-(7-8)+9A^*-B)$	$BA-9+8+7+6^*5+432^*1$
0561	00793	$-1-(-234-(-5-(678-9AB)))$	$-BA+987-6-5+4-321$
0562	00794	$12-3+456-(7-8-(9+AB))$	$-B-A-(-98-7-65-432)+1$
0563	00795	$12-34+567-(8-9)-(-A-B)$	$BA-98-(7-(6+543))-(-2-1)$
0564	00796	$-123-4-5-6+789-AB$	$B+A9+87^*6+(5-4)^*-32^*-1$
0565	00797	$1+2+3-(4-(567+8))-(-9+A+B)$	$B-A+987+6+5+432^*-1$
0566	00798	$-1-23+4-5+678-(9A+B)$	$BA9-8-(7+654-3-21)$
0567	00799	$-12+34-(56+7)^*-8+9^*(A+B)$	$B+A-9-87+654-32^*1$
0568	00800	$-12-34+5+678-9A+B$	$BA+9-87+6+543-21$
0569	00801	$1234+5+6-(7-(-89A+B))$	$B-A-98-7+654-3-2^*1$
056A	00802	$1-2+3-456+7+8+9AB$	$-B+A98+765+4^*-321$
056B	00803	$-1+234-(-5+678-9AB)$	$-B-A-(98-7-654)+3+2^*1$
0570	00804	$-1^*(-234-5+678-9AB)$	$BA9-8^*-7-(654+32)+1$
0571	00805	$12-(3+4)-(-567-8)-9^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A9-87-6+543+21$
0572	00806	$1^*-23-(-4+5-678)-(-9+AB)$	$BA9-8+7-654-3+21$
0573	00807	$12-(3+45-678)-(9A-B)$	$BA9-8-(7+654-32)-1$
0574	00808	$-12-3+4+567-8+9+A+B$	$BA-9-8-76+543+2^*1$
0575	00809	$-1+234-(567-89A)+B$	$-BA-98+765-(-4-(3-21))$
0576	00810	$-1-2+3^*456+7+8^*(-9-AB)$	$-BA+98+76+543-21$
0577	00811	$1234+5-6-789-AB$	$BA-98+7-(-6-543-2+1)$
0578	00812	$1-23+456+7^*8-(-9-AB)$	$B-(-A+9+87-654)-(3^*2-1)$
0579	00813	$-123+4+567-8+9^*(A+B)$	$BA9+87-654-3^*21$
057A	00814	$-123+4-5+678-(-9-A-B)$	$BA+98+76+5+4+321$
057B	00815	$-1-(-2-(-34+5))-(-678-(-9A+B))$	$BA+98+7^*65-4-3+21$
0580	00816	$1-2+3+4+567-(-8+9)-A-B$	$-B+A-98+7+654-3+2-1$
0581	00817	$1-(23-4)-(-5-678-9)-AB$	$-B+A98+7^*6-(543-2+1)$
0582	00818	$12-34-5+678-9A+B$	$B+A-98+7+654+3-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0583	00819	-1+2-3-4-(-567+89)+AB	BA9-8-76-(543+21)
0584	00820	12-345-6+7-8+9A*B	BA-9+8-(76-543)+2*-1
0585	00821	-1+2-3+4-(-56*-7-89A-B)	BA9-8-(-7+654-32+1)
0586	00822	1-(2-34)+567-8-(9+A)+B	B-(-A-98)-7-(-65-(432+1))
0587	00823	12-345-(-6-7-89A-B)	BA9+8-7-(654-32)-1
0588	00824	-12-(3-4-567-8-9)-(-A-B)	-B-(A9+8-(7+654))-(-32+1)
0589	00825	-1+23+4-(-567-8)-(-9+A+B)	-B+A9+87-6-(5-432-1)
058A	00826	-1+2+3-(45+6*78)+9AB	-B-(A9-8+7-(654+32-1))
058B	00827	-1*(23-4+5-678-9-A*-B)	-BA-9+8*7+(-654-3*-2)*-1
0590	00828	-1*-2*(345+6+7-89+A+B)	BA9+8-(-7+654-3-21)
0591	00829	-1-(234-56)-(-789+A+B)	BA-9-8-7*6+543-21
0592	00830	-12-(345+6)-(78-9AB)	-B-A+9+8-7-6*-54+321
0593	00831	12-3*45*-6-7-8+9-AB	BA-9-(8+76)-(-543-21)
0594	00832	123-(-456+7+89-AB)	-B+A98+7+6*-5*4*3*-2*-1
0595	00833	-1+2+3+4+567-89+AB	-BA+98+76+543+2*-1
0596	00834	123+45+6-7*-89-AB	-B-(A+9-(-87+654)-32-1)
0597	00835	-123+4+567-8*-9+AB	-B-A-(-9+87)+654-3+21
0598	00836	1+2-3+4+5+678-9A-B	BA-9-87*-6-5*-4*3+21
0599	00837	-12-3+4+567-8*-9-A-B	-B+A98-(76+5+432-1)
059A	00838	-12+3+4*56+7*(-8*-9+A)+B	BA9+8+7-654-32*-1
059B	00839	123-4+567-8-9-A*B	-B-A-987-6+5*(-4+321)
05A0	00840	-1-23+4*56-7*-89-AB	B+A-98+7+654-3+2+1
05A1	00841	-1-2-345-6-(78-9AB)	B-(-A+9*(-87+6))-(-5+43-2-1)
05A2	00842	-1-2-(3-4)-(5-678)-(9A-B)	-BA+98-7*-6*-5*-4+3+21
05A3	00843	-1+23-4+5+678-9-AB	-B-(A-9-(87+6))-(-543+21)
05A4	00844	-12-(34-567+8-9A+B)	-B-(A-9+8-76-543-2-1)
05A5	00845	-1-(-2-3-456-(78-(-9A+B)))	B+A9+87-6-5+432-1
05A6	00846	1*2*-3*(-45-6-78+9-A+B)	-B+A98-7-65-432-1
05A7	00847	-123+45+6+78*9+AB	-BA+9+8+7+654+32-1
05A8	00848	1+2*(345-6)-7-(89+A)+B	BA9-87+6-543+2+1
05A9	00849	-123-45-(-6-(-7-8))*-9A+B	BA-9+8+76-(-5-432+1)
05AA	00850	-123+45-(-6-7+8*-9A-B)	BA9+87-654+32*-1
05AB	00851	-1-23-(4-567-(89-A)+B)	BA+987-(65+432-1)
05B0	00852	-1-(23-(45+678-9A)+B)	-B-A-9+87+6+543-2*-1
05B1	00853	12-(3-4)+5-(-678+9A+B)	-BA-(98-765-43)-21
05B2	00854	-1+23-4+5+678-9A-B	BA-(9-876+54+321)
05B3	00855	1+2-(-345+6)-(-7*-8*-9+AB)	-B+A-(9+87-(-6-5)*-4*(-3+21))
05B4	00856	12-(34-5)-(-678-9*-A-B)	B-A-9-(87-(654-(-32-1)))
05B5	00857	-12-345-67-(-8-9AB)	-B+A+9+876+54-321
05B6	00858	-1*(-2+345-6-(-78+9AB))	BA+9-(-8-7-65)-(-432-1)
05B7	00859	1234+5+67-89A-B	BA+9+8-(-76+5)+432+1
05B8	00860	123+4+567+8+9-AB	BA-9-(-87-6-5)-(-432+1)
05B9	00861	1-2+34-5+678-9A-B	-B-(-A-9+87-654-3-21)
05BA	00862	1+2+3+456+78-9+AB	B-A9-(-8-(7+654))-(-32+1)
05BB	00863	-123+45+6-(7+8+9*-A*B)	-B-A9-(-87-654)-3-21
0600	00864	-1+2-34+567+89+A-B	BA9-876-54+321
0601	00865	12-345-6+(7+89A)*B	-B-(A98-7+6+54*-32+1)
0602	00866	-1+2-(34-567-89)-(A-B)	BA-(-9-87+6-5)+432-1
0603	00867	-1+2-(3-45)+678-(9+AB)	-BA-(-9-8)-(-7*65+4)+321
0604	00868	-123+4+567+89+AB	BA+9+87-(6-5)-(-432-1)
0605	00869	-12+3+45+678-9A-B	-BA-(-9+8-7-654)-3*-21
0606	00870	12-(345-6-(-78+9AB))	BA+9*8-(76-543)-21
0607	00871	-1-234-(-56-789-(A+B))	B-A-9+87+6+543-2+1
0608	00872	12-34+567-8+9A-B	-B-(-A+9-87-6-543-2*1)
0609	00873	-1-2-34-56+789-AB	B+A-(-9-87-(-6+543)+21)
060A	00874	1+2-(345-(-67+8+9AB))	B-A9+87+654-32-1
060B	00875	-1+2-3-456+78+9AB	B-(A-9-87+6)-(-543+2+1)
0610	00876	-1+2*-345*(6-7)+8-(-9+A*B)	B-A9+87+654-32+1
0611	00877	1+2+3-(-4-(-5+6-7*-89)-AB)	B-A9*8-(7-65-4*321)
0612	00878	12-3-45-6-7+8*9A-B	-BA-9+87+654-3+2-1
0613	00879	-1-2*-34+56+7+(8-9)*A+B	-B+A+9+8+76+543+2*1
0614	00880	-12+34-(-5-678-(-9A+B))	B-(-A-9+8*7-654)+3-21
0615	00881	-1+2-(34-567+8)+9A+B	-BA-(-98-(7+654))-3-21
0616	00882	-123-45-6-(-789-A+B)	-B-A-9*-87-(-6-5+4)*-3-(2+1)
0617	00883	-1-23-(45-678-9)-(-A+B)	-B-(-A9-8)-(7+6-543+2)+1
0618	00884	1+23+456+78-(9-AB)	BA9+87-654-3-2+1
0619	00885	-1-23-(45-678)-(-9+A-B)	B-A9+87+654-3-21
061A	00886	1-23-4-56+789-AB	B-A9+8-7+654+3*21
061B	00887	-1-2*3*(-4-5)+678+9-AB	-B-A98+7*-6+54*(32+1)
0620	00888	1-(2-(-34-5-6))-(-7-8*9A+B)	BA9+87-(654-3)-2-1
0621	00889	-12-34-5-(-678+9A-B)	BA+98+7+6+5+432-1
0622	00890	-12+34+5*-67+89A-B	B+A-(-987+65-4)-321
0623	00891	1+2+3+456+7+89+AB	B+A9-(8+7-(-6+543))-(-2+1)
0624	00892	1+234+567-(89+AB)	-B+A-98+765-43-21
0625	00893	12+34+5+678-(-9+AB)	B+A+9-(87-654-32*1)
0626	00894	-12-34-(5+6)-(-78*-9-AB)	-B+A9+876-5-4-321
0627	00895	12+3*-4-56+7*(8+9A+B)	-BA-(-9+8-(765-43))+2*1
0628	00896	-1-2-3+45+678-9A+B	B+A+98+7+6+543-21
0629	00897	-1+23+456-7+89+AB	B-(-A-(9+8+76))+543-2*1
062A	00898	-123-(4+5-(678-9))+AB	BA-9+8*76-(5-43+2-1)
062B	00899	-1-2*(3+4+5-678)+9*-A*B	-B-A+9*(8+76)-5-(-4-32-1)
0630	00900	-1-(-2+3-45)-(-678+9A-B)	-BA-9+8-7*(-6+5+4*(-32+1))
0631	00901	-123+4-56+789+A+B	BA-(-9+87)-(-654-3*-21)
0632	00902	1-23-(-45-6*-78)+9AB	-BA+9-8+765-4+32*-1
0633	00903	12-3-(4+56)+7*-8*-9A+B	B+A9-8-7+6+543+2-1
0634	00904	-12-34+5-(6+78*-9-AB)	B-(-A+9-8+7-654+32-1)
0635	00905	1+23-456+78+9AB	-B+A*-9-8+765+4+3*-21
0636	00906	-1+23+45+678-9A-B	-B-(A-987-(-6-5-4-321))
0637	00907	123-4+567+8*9-AB	-B-(A-987+654)+321
0638	00908	1234-(56+789-A)+B	BA-(9+8+7)-(-6-543)+21
0639	00909	-1-2-(34-5+(678-9))*(A-B))	B+A9*8-(76-5+43)+2*1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
063A	00910	$123+4^*-56-(-789-A^*-B)$	$BA-98-7+654-32+1$
063B	00911	$1-(2-34+56)-(78^*-9+A^*-B)$	$-BA-(-9-8)-(-765+43)-2^*-1$
0640	00912	$-1-2-(-345-6^*78)-(-9+AB)$	$BA-(98-76)-(-543-21)$
0641	00913	$12-(3-(45+678))-(-9A-B)$	$-B+A98-765-(4-321)$
0642	00914	$1-23+4-(-567-8)+9A+B$	$BA+9-8-7+6+543+2-1$
0643	00915	$-12-34-(-5-678)-(-9-A+B)$	$BA-9+8^*(76-5)+43^*2^*1$
0644	00916	$-123-(4-5)-(6-789-(-A-B))$	$B-A-(-9-8-7)+654-(32-1)$
0645	00917	$-12-34+5-(-678-9+A-B)$	$B+A+987+6-5^*43^*2+1$
0646	00918	$1-2-(34+56+7+8^*(-9A-B))$	$-BA+9-(8-765-(-43+21))$
0647	00919	$12+3-(-45-678+9A)+B$	$BA9-876-5-(4-321)$
0648	00920	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4)^*(-567+89A-B)$	$BA-9-(87-(654+32^*-1))$
0649	00921	$1-(-2-3+4+5^*(-67-89))+A-B$	$B+A-9^*8^*(-7-6)-54+3+21$
064A	00922	$12-3-45+678+9A-B$	$-B-(A+98-765+43-21)$
064B	00923	$-12-345-6-7+8+9AB$	$-B+A9+8^*-76-(54-3)^*-21$
0650	00924	$12-(-34-567+8-9^*A+B)$	$-B+A98-7+6-5-432-1$
0651	00925	$1-2-(3-4-5+6-(-7-8^*-9A-B))$	$B-A9+8+765-43+2-1$
0652	00926	$12+34-56-78^*-9-A^*-B$	$-B-A9-87^*-6-5-4+321$
0653	00927	$12-34+5+678-(9-(-A+B))$	$BA+9+876-5-4-321$
0654	00928	$1-234+5-(-6-789)+AB$	$B+A+987-6-(5-(-4-321))$
0655	00929	$1-2^*(-345+6)+78+9-AB$	$B-(A-9+8+7-(654+3)-2)+1$
0656	00930	$1-(2+34+5+6-789)-AB$	$-B-(A9-87)+654+32+1$
0657	00931	$1234-5-6-789+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9)-(-876+54^*(3+2)-1)$
0658	00932	$1-2-34-(-5-678+9-(A+B))$	$-B+A-98+765+4^*3^*(-2-1)$
0659	00933	$12+3-4+567-8+9A+B$	$BA-98+7-(-654+3+21)$
065A	00934	$1-(2-(-345-(6-7+8)+9AB))$	$-BA-9+8+765-4-3-2+1$
065B	00935	$1-(23+4^*-56+78^*-9)-AB$	$-B+A9+8+7+6+543+21$
0660	00936	$12+34+5+678-(9^*A-B)$	$-B+A98-(7-6-5)-(432-1)$
0661	00937	$-12-(-3+45^*6-(7+89A-B))$	$-BA+98+7+654-(-3-21)$
0662	00938	$12-3-4+567-(8-9)+AB$	$B-(-A+98)+765-(43-(-2+1))$
0663	00939	$-1^*(234-(-5+6)-(7+89A)+B)$	$BA+9-(87-654+32)+1$
0664	00940	$-1-234-56-(78-9AB)$	$B-A9+8+765+4-32-1$
0665	00941	$-1-2-3^*-456-789+AB$	$B-(A9-8)-(-765-4-32^*-1)$
0666	00942	$-12-3-45+67+8^*9A-B$	$-B-A-(-9^*87-(-6+54+3)+21)$
0667	00943	$1+2^*(345-67)+8-9+AB$	$B+A98-(765-(4+321))$
0668	00944	$1+2-34-5+678+9-(-A-B)$	$B+A98-(7+6-5)-(432+1)$
0669	00945	$1234-5+6-789-A+B$	$-BA-9+8+765-(-4+3+2^*-1)$
066A	00946	$12-3-45+6+789-AB$	$BA9-8-7-6-543+21$
066B	00947	$1^*-23+4-(-5-6+78^*-9-AB)$	$B-(A-(9+8+7)-654)-(-3+2+1)$
0670	00948	$12-(3-4-5)-(6+7^*8-9^*-A^*-B)$	$-B-(-A-987-6)-(-5+4)-321$
0671	00949	$-1-2-3+4-(-5-678+9)-(-A+B)$	$BA-9+8^*(7-6)^*(54+32^*)^*1$
0672	00950	$-1^*2^*(-3+456-789+A-B)$	$-BA-9-(8-765+4)-(-3-21)$
0673	00951	$12-345-6-7+8+9AB$	$B-A9+87+654+32^*1$
0674	00952	$12+3-(-4+5-678)-(-9-(-A-B))$	$BA9+8-7+6-543+2+1$
0675	00953	$-1-2-(-345+678-9AB)$	$BA-9-(-8-7^*6-543-(-2+1))$
0676	00954	$1-(-23+45^*6-(789+AB))$	$BA+9-87+654+3-21$
0677	00955	$-12+3-4^*-5+678-9+A-B$	$-B-(A9-876-5)+4^*32^*-1$
0678	00956	$-123+4+5+6+789+A-B$	$B-(-A98-(-76-54)+321)$
0679	00957	$-1+2-(-345+678)+9AB$	$BA+98+7+65+432+1$
067A	00958	$1234-5-6+78-9^*AB$	$-BA+9-(-8-765)-(-4-(3-2+1))$
067B	00959	$12+34+567+89-A+B$	$-B+A-98+765-(4+3)-2^*1$
0680	00960	$-1-23-4^*-5+678-(9-A-B)$	$B-A+9-8-7+654+32-1$
0681	00961	$1-2-3+4-5+678+9-A+B$	$BA-98+7+654-3+2+1$
0682	00962	$-1+2-(-34+5-678+9+A+B)$	$BA9+8-(7+6)-(543-21)$
0683	00963	$-1+234-5+6+7^*-8^*-9+AB$	$BA^*98-(-7-6+5)^*(-43+21)$
0684	00964	$123+45+6-(7^*-89-(A-B))$	$B+A-(9+87)+654+3-(-2-1)$
0685	00965	$-1-2+3+4-5+678+9-A+B$	$B-A+9-8-(-7-(654+3))+21$
0686	00966	$1^*(23-4)^*(56-7-8-9)^*(-A+B)$	$-B-A9+8^*7^*6+543-2+1$
0687	00967	$123-45-(-678-(-9A+B))$	$-B-(-A9-(-87+654+3-(2-1)))$
0688	00968	$12+3+4+567-(-8-9-AB)$	$BA+98+765+5+432+1$
0689	00969	$1-(-2-(3+4-5+678+9+A)+B)$	$-B-A9-8+765+4+3+21$
068A	00970	$12+345-678+9AB$	$B-(-A98-7)-(-6-5+432)-1$
068B	00971	$123-456+7+8+9AB$	$-B+A9-8-(76+543)^*(-2+1)$
0690	00972	$-12-34-(-56-789+A)-B$	$-B+A+9-8+7+654-(-32+1)$
0691	00973	$-1-2-345+6^*7-(8-9AB)$	$B-(-A9-8)-76^*5+43^*21$
0692	00974	$12-(-34-567)-(8-(9A+B))$	$-B-A9^*(-8-7)-(654-3+21)$
0693	00975	$-1+23+4+5^*-6-7-8-9^*-A^*B$	$BA9-(-8-7-6)-(-5^*4^*-32-1)$
0694	00976	$-1-(-2-3^*45-678)-(-9+AB)$	$-BA-9-8+765-(-43+2)+1$
0695	00977	$12-(345-6-7-8-9AB)$	$B+A98-7+6^*5-432+1$
0696	00978	$-1-2-34-56-78-9^*-AB$	$-BA-98-(-765-(-4^*-32-1))$
0697	00979	$-1-2+3-4-5-(-6-789+AB)$	$-B+A-(9+8^*-7)-(-654-3^*2+1)$
0698	00980	$-123-(-45-6-789+A+B)$	$B+A+9-8-(7-654)-(-32+1)$
0699	00981	$1-23-4^*56+78+9^*AB$	$-B+A9-(87-654+32^*-1)$
069A	00982	$123-4+567-(-8-(9+A-B))$	$-B-A+9+87+654-32+1$
069B	00983	$1-234+56+789+AB$	$B-A9-8-(-765+4-(3+21))$
06A0	00984	$12+3+4-5+678-9+A+B$	$BA9-87-6-5-432-1$
06A1	00985	$12+34-(-5-678+9)-(A+B)$	$-BA+9-8-(-765-4)-(-32+1)$
06A2	00986	$-1-23-4-5^*6-(7-8+9)^*-AB$	$-BA-9+87^*(6+5)+4+3-(2+1)$
06A3	00987	$-12+34-5-(-678-(9-A)-B)$	$-BA-(-9+8)-(-765-4-32-1)$
06A4	00988	$-1-2-(-3-(-4-5))-(-6^*7-89^*A+B)$	$B-A-98+765-4-3+21$
06A5	00989	$-1-234-(-56+7)+89A-B$	$-B-A9-8+765+43+2-1$
06A6	00990	$1^*-234-(-56+7-89A)-B$	$-B^*-A^*-9^*(8-76+5-(-43-21))$
06A7	00991	$1-23-(-45-678-9-A+B)$	$-B-A+987+6^*-54-3^*(2-1)$
06A8	00992	$1-(2-34-5-678)-(9+A-B)$	$BA9-876+54+321$
06A9	00993	$-1+23-4+5-(-678-9+A-B)$	$B+A9-87-(-654-3-21)$
06AA	00994	$-1-(-2-3)-(-4+5+6-7-8+9^*-A^*B)$	$-B+A9-8-7+654-32+1$
06AB	00995	$-1^*(23+45-678-(-9+A^*-B)))$	$-B-(A+9-(87+654))-3^*2^*1$
06B0	00996	$-1+2-34+567+89+AB$	$BA-(9+87-(654+32^*1))$
06B1	00997	$-1+2-34-5-67-8^*(-9-AB)$	$-BA-(-987-(-6-5^*43))-(-2+1)$
06B2	00998	$12-3-4^*5+6-(-78-9+A)^*B$	$BA-98+7-(-654-32)-1$
06B3	00999	$1234-5-(6+7)+89^*-A+B$	$B-(-A9+8^*-7-6^*(-54-3)^*-2+1)$
06B4	01000	$-1-23+4+5^*-67-8+9AB$	$BA-98+7+654+32+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
06B5	01001	-1-23+45-6+789-AB	-BA-9+876-5*(-4-3+21)
06B6	01002	-1-(23-4)-(56-789+A)-B	-B-(A-(987+65))-(-4+321)
06B7	01003	1-23+45-6+789-AB	BA-(-987-65)-(432+1)
06B8	01004	-1-2-3-45+678-(-9A+B)	BA-(9-87)-(6-543-2-1)
06B9	01005	1-(-234-5)-(6*(-7-89)-A)-B	-BA+98+765-43-2-1
06BA	01006	1-234-5+67+89A-B	BA9-87-(-6-5)-(432+1)
06BB	01007	12+34+5+678-(9A-B)	-BA+98-(-765+43-(-2+1))
0700	01008	12-3+45-(-678-9)-(A+B)	B+A9-(-8-76)-(-543+2)+1
0701	01009	1-234-5-(-6-(-78+9AB))	B+A9+87+6-5*-4*-32*-1
0702	01010	-123-4-(-5-(-67+89A-B))	B-A+98-(7-654)-(3+21)
0703	01011	-1+2-3+45-67-89*-A-B	B+A98-(76+5+4+321)
0704	01012	-1+234+567+8+9-AB	BA9+8-76-5+432*-1
0705	01013	1-234+56-7+89A+B	-BA-(-9-8-765)-(-43-2*1)
0706	01014	-12-(345+6-78-9AB)	BA-(-987+6+54)-321
0707	01015	-12-3-45+678+9A+B	-B-A+9-8+765-43+2-1
0708	01016	1-(-2-34)-(-5-678+9-A)+B	-B-A-(-9*87-65+4-32+1)
0709	01017	12+3-4*56+7*89-A+B	BA9+8*7-(6+543-21)
070A	01018	1-(234-5)-(67+8)+9AB	-BA-(-98-765+4+32-1)
070B	01019	-1+2-3-(-45-678-(-9+A))+B	-B+A-9-(-87-654-(-3+2))+1
0710	01020	-123+4*5-(6-7)*8-9*-AB	-B-A+987-6*5*-4*3-2*-1
0711	01021	-1+2*-3*45-(67+8)+9AB	B+A98-76-(-5-(-4-321))
0712	01022	1+234-(-567+89-A)-B	BA9-(8-7)-65-432+1
0713	01023	123+456+7+8*9+AB	-B+A9-(-87-6-(543+21))
0714	01024	1-(23-(45-6))-(-789-A*-B)	B-A+987+65+4-321
0715	01025	1-2-(3-45+6)+789-AB	BA-9+8-7+654-32+1
0716	01026	1-23+4-56+789-A+B	BA9+87-(-6-(-543-21))
0717	01027	12-345-(-67+8-9AB)	BA-(9-8-(76-(-543-21)))
0718	01028	1-(23+45-(-6+789*(-A+B)))	B-(A+9+8-765+4+32)+1
0719	01029	-1+2-345-6+78+9AB	-B-A9-(-8-765-43-21)
071A	01030	-12-(-3-45)-(-6-789+AB)	B+A9*8-7-6-5*(-4+3+2-1)
071B	01031	1+2-3-(4-567-89-AB)	-BA-(9-876+54-3-2)-1
0720	01032	12-3-(-4-5)-(-67+8*-9A)-B	B-A9+876-(54+3+21)
0721	01033	-12-(-3+4)-(56-(789-A)-B)	BA+9+8-7+6-5*(4+3)*-21
0722	01034	123-(-456-78-9A)+B	BA9+8-7*65+4*(-32+1)
0723	01035	1-2-(3-(4+567+89+AB))	B+A-9-876+5*(-4+321)
0724	01036	-1-(-23+45)-(-678-9A+B)	BA-(9+8+76*5-(-4+321))
0725	01037	-12-3-4-5+678+9A-B	-B+A9+8+765-(43-2-1)
0726	01038	-12+34+5*6+789-AB	-BA+9+876+5-43-21
0727	01039	-1-(2-3-(4+567-(-89-AB)))	B-(-A98-76)-5-(432-1)
0728	01040	123+45+678-(9+AB)	B+A98-76-5*-4-321
0729	01041	-1-(23+4)-5+678-(-9-AB)	B+A9-(-8+7-(654-3)+21)
072A	01042	-1+234+567-(89-A-B)	-BA9-(8+7*6*5+4+3*-21)
072B	01043	1-23-(-4+5-678+9-AB)	B-(A9-876+5-(-43-21))
0730	01044	-1-(-23-(45+678)+9*(A-B))	-B+A-98+765+43+21
0731	01045	-1+2-(-3+4-(5-6))+7*8-9*A*-B	-B+A9-(8-7-654+3-2-1)
0732	01046	1-(23-4)-56-(-789-A-B)	BA-(9+8)-(7-654*(-3+2))*-1
0733	01047	12+3+4-56-(-789+A+B)	-B-A+9-8+765+4-(-3+21)
0734	01048	123-456+78+9AB	-B-(-A-98-7-654-(-3+2-1))
0735	01049	-12-34+5+6-(-789+A+B)	BA9-8+76-543+21
0736	01050	12-(3-(4+567))-(-89+AB)	BA+9+876-(-5-4)*-32-1
0737	01051	-1+2-3-45*6-7*8+9AB	B-(-A9+8-7)+654-3*-2*1
0738	01052	-1-2-(-3+4)*-5*(67-8-(-9-AB))	B-(A-9+8-765)-(-4+32+1)
0739	01053	-1*-23*(-4+56-78-9)*(A-B)	B+A+9-8+765-43-2-1
073A	01054	-12+3-(4+5-6-7+89*-A-B)	-B-A-9+876-5-43*(2+1)
073B	01055	12-(34+5+6)-(-789+A)-B	-B-A+9+8+765-43+21
0740	01056	-123-4-56+7-8-9A*-B	-BA-(-9+876-54*32+1)
0741	01057	12-(-3+45-6+78-9*AB)	BA-98+765-43-2-1
0742	01058	1-2-3+4-5+678+9A-B	-B+A-(-98+7-654-(-3+21))
0743	01059	-12+34-5-(-6+7-89*A+B)	-B+A9-(-8-765+4*-32*-1)
0744	01060	1-2+3-45+67+8*(9A+B)	B+A98-7*65-(-4-3)+21
0745	01061	12-3+4-56+789+A-B	B-A9+876-(54-(3-2*1))
0746	01062	-123+45-(67-89A+B)	-B-(-A9-(87+6*54+321))
0747	01063	-123+4+56-7-(8+9*-AB)	-B+A-9-(8-765)-4-(-3+2+1)
0748	01064	-1-(-234+5-6-7*89A)+B	-B-A9+876+5-(-4+32+1)
0749	01065	-1*(-2+34+5+6-789+A-B)	-B+A9-8*7+654+3*21
074A	01066	-1-(23-4-(5+678+9A+B))	B-A9+876-5-43+2*-1
074B	01067	1*-23+4+5+678+9A+B	-B-A-(-98-7)-(-654-32+1)
0750	01068	1+2-34+56+7-8*(-9A-B)	BA-9*-87-65-(-43-21)
0751	01069	-12-34+5+6+789+A-B	B+A9-8+765-4*(32-1)
0752	01070	123-4+567+89+A-B	-BA-9+876+5-43+21
0753	01071	-123-(4-56-(-7+8))+9*AB	B+A-9-8+765+4+3-21
0754	01072	1+2*(-345+678)+9A+B	BA9-87-65-4-321
0755	01073	-1-(-2+3+45)-(-6-(789+A+B))	BA9-87+65-432*1
0756	01074	1-(234-56+78-9AB)	-B+A98-7-6-5+4-321
0757	01075	1234-5+6-789+AB	-B-A9-87*6+5-4*-321
0758	01076	1*-2*(-345-67-(89-AB))	B-A9+876-(5-(-4-32)+1)
0759	01077	-123-4+(5-6)*(7-89A+B)	-B-(-A-9)-8+765-(4+3+2-1)
075A	01078	1+2-(-34-567-89-AB)	BA-(98-765-4+32-1)
075B	01079	1-23+4-(5+6)-(-789-(A-B))	-BA+9-8*-7+6+(5-43)*-21
0760	01080	-123-45+6-(7-8)*-9A*-B	BA9-87-(65-4+321)
0761	01081	12+3-4+5+678+9A-B	BA9-876-(5-(432+1))
0762	01082	12+3-(45-6-789-A+B)	BA-9+8+7+654-3*2*-1
0763	01083	1234-5-678+9-A-B	-B-A9+876+5+4-3-21
0764	01084	123+45-6-7*-89+AB	B-(-A+9-(8+76*5))-432*-1
0765	01085	-1*(2-34-(-56+789))*(-A+B)	BA-98+765-4+3-21
0766	01086	123-45+6+7-8*-9A+B	BA+9+8-7+654+3+2+1
0767	01087	12-3-4-5-(-678-9A)+B	BA-98+765+4-3-21
0768	01088	12-3+4-(5-678)-9+AB	-BA-9+876-5+4-(3-(2-1))
0769	01089	-1+2+3-(-4+5+6-789+A+B)	BA9-876+5+432-1
076A	01090	-12+345-(6-7*89)-A*B	BA-9+8-(7-(654+3+21))
076B	01091	1-(23-4+56*(-7+8))-9*-AB	B-(A-98)-(-7-654)-(-32-1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0770	01092	-12-(3+4)-(5-6-789-A+B)	BA9+87*-6-5-4-3*-2*1
0771	01093	-12+34+(5+6+7-89-A)*-B	-B-(-A98-7)-(-6*-54-3*-21)
0772	01094	1+2-3-45*6-(7+8-9AB)	BA9-8-76-54-321
0773	01095	-1-(2-34)-(5-678-9A)-B	B+A98-765+432-1
0774	01096	-123+4-(-5-6-(-7+89A)+B)	-BA-(-987-(6+54*-3)-21)
0775	01097	1-2+3+4+5-(6-789)-(A+B)	B-A9-(-876+54-32+1)
0776	01098	1-(-2-(34+56))-(-7+8+9*-A*B)	BA-(-9-8)-(-7-654-3-2)-1
0777	01099	-12-(-34+5)+678-(9-AB)	B+A98-7*(6+54)-3+21
0778	01100	-1+234+567+89-AB	-B+A-9-8-(-765+4-32)-1
0779	01101	-1-2*(-34+56)*(-7-89+AB)	B+A+9-8-(-765-(-4-3-(-2+1)))
077A	01102	12-(-34+56-(789-(A-B)))	-BA-(9-876)-(-54-3*21)
077B	01103	-12-34-56+789-A*-B	B-A9+876+5-43+21
0780	01104	123-45+678+9+A+B	B-A*9+8*(76+54-3)-21
0781	01105	-1-(-23+4-5)+678-9+AB	B+A9+8+7+654-3+21
0782	01106	-12+34-5+678+9A+B	-B-A-(-9*87-6)-(54*-3-2*1)
0783	01107	1+23-4+5+678-9+AB	B-(-A+9+87)-(-65-43*21)
0784	01108	1+2-(-3-4)-(56+7-(-8-9*-AB))	-BA+98+7-(6*54*-3+21)
0785	01109	1234+56*7+8-9AB	B+A-9+8+765+4-(-3+2)-1
0786	01110	1+23*-4*-5-6*(-78+9-A)+B	B+A-98+7-65+43*21
0787	01111	1-(23-4-5)-(6-789)-(-A-B)	B-A-(9-8-765-43+21)
0788	01112	1+2*(345-6)-7*8+(9+A)*B	BA9+87*-6-(-5*-4-32)-1
0789	01113	-12-3-(-4+5-(-67-(8-9A)*B))	-B-A+9-8+765+43-2-1
078A	01114	1+23-(45-6-(7+8-9A)*-B)	-B-A+9-(8-765-43)-2*1
078B	01115	-1234+5*-67*-8*(-9+A)+B	B+A-9-8+765+4-(3-21)
0790	01116	-1*(23+4)*(-5+6*7+8*-9+A-B)	-BA-(-9-8-765+4*(-32-1))
0791	01117	-12+34-5+678+9+AB	-BA-9+876+54+32*-1
0792	01118	-12+3+45-(6-78)+9*A*B	-B+A+9-8+765-4+32-1
0793	01119	-1+23+45-(6-7*8-9*A*B)	-B+A9-8+765-(43+21)
0794	01120	-1-2+34+5+678-(9-AB)	B+A9-(-8-7-654)-(-32+1)
0795	01121	-1+2+3+4+5-6+78-9*-AB	B-(-A9-8)+765+4*(-3-21)
0796	01122	1+234+5+67-8*9*-A-B	-BA+9-(-876-5)+4-(-3-(2-1))
0797	01123	-1-(23-45-(6+789-A))-B	B-A9-(-876-5)-(-4+3)+2-1
0798	01124	123-(-4-5)-(-678-9+A)-B	BA9+87-(65+432+1)
0799	01125	1-2-3*-45+678*(-9+A)+B	-B-A9+876+5-(4-(-3+21))
079A	01126	1-(234+56)+78+9AB	BA9+87-65-(432-1)
079B	01127	1-(2+3*4)-56-(78-9A*B)	-B+A-(-9-8-765-43+21)
07A0	01128	-1+234+567-8+9-A+B	-BA+98+76*-5-4-(-32+1)
07A1	01129	-1*(2-34-5-(-6+789-A-B))	-BA-9+876+5-4+32-1
07A2	01130	12+34-5-6-78+9*A*B	-B+A9+876-5*43+21
07A3	01131	1+234+56+7*89-A+B	B-A9*-8+76-(-5-(-4-(-3+2)))*-1
07A4	01132	-123-45-(67-8-9AB)	B+A9+8+765+43*-2+1
07A5	01133	1-23+45-6+789+A-B	B-(-A9+8+7-6+(-5+43)*-21)
07A6	01134	1234-56-7*89-AB	-BA-98-(-7-654)+321
07A7	01135	-12-34-(-5-6)+7-(-8+9*-AB)	-BA+98+765+43+21
07A8	01136	123-4+5+678+9+A-B	-BA+9-(-876+5)-(-4-3-21)
07A9	01137	123-4*5+678+9+A+B	BA-98+765+43-21
07AA	01138	123-4-5-6-(-789+AB)	BA-(-987-6*(5+4))-321
07AB	01139	1*234-5-(-678+9+AB)	BA9-(87+654-321)
07B0	01140	1-2+34-5-6+789+A-B	-BA-(9-876+5)+43-(-2-1)
07B1	01141	1-2+3-4*(-5+67)-(-8-9AB)	BA+9*87-(-6-54)-(-3-(-2+1))
07B2	01142	-1+23-4*-5+678+9+AB	B-A*-9-8*(7+6)*-5*(-4+3)*-2+1
07B3	01143	-123-(-4-56)-(-789-AB)	-BA-98+7-6+(5+43)*21
07B4	01144	-1*-2*(-3+45-6)*78-(-9*-A-B))	BA+98-(-76-543-21)
07B5	01145	-12-3+4+56+789-A-B	-BA-(-9-876)-(-54+3+21)
07B6	01146	1+234+567+8+9-A+B	B-A+9+8+765+4+32+1
07B7	01147	1-(2+3)+45-(-6-789+A+B)	-B+A9+87+654-3+2-1
07B8	01148	-1*(-2+3+45+67-89A-B)	BA-(98-765-4*3-21)
07B9	01149	12-3+45+678-(-9A-B)	B-(-A9-(87+654+3-21))
07BA	01150	1234+56-(789-AB)	-BA-9+876-(-54+3)+2*-1
07BB	01151	-1+2-(-3+45+6)-(-78-9A*B)	-BA+9+876-(-54-3)-21
0800	01152	-12+3*-4+56+789+A-B	-B+A+9+876-(-5+43*2+1)
0801	01153	12-(-3+4+5)-6*7+8-9*-AB	-BA+9-(-876+5-43+2*1)
0802	01154	-1*-2*(-34-5+67*8-(9-A)-B)	-B-A-9+876-5-43+2*-1
0803	01155	12+3+45+678+9A+B	B-A+9+876+5-43*2*1
0804	01156	-1+234-5+678+9-AB	BA9-8-7+65*(-4-3)-2-1
0805	01157	-12-3-(4-(-56+789)))+AB	BA+987+65-4-321
0806	01158	-1+2-34-(5-(-67+89A+B))	BA-9-8+765-43-2+1
0807	01159	-1+23-45-(-6+7-8-9*AB)	-BA+987-6-(54-(-3-21))
0808	01160	12-(3+45)-67-(-89A-B)	BA98-7*-65*4*3*(-2-1)
0809	01161	-12+34-5+6+789+A+B	B+A+9-87*(-6-5)+4-3-2-1
080A	01162	-1+2+3-45-67-8-9A*-B	-BA+9+876-(-5-43+2+1)
080B	01163	-12+3-4-56+789+AB	-B-(-A9+8-765+4-(-3-21))
0810	01164	-1-234-(5-67+8)+9AB	B-A9-87+654+321
0811	01165	-12-3-(-4-56)-(-789-A+B)	-B-(-A98-7-6-54+321)
0812	01166	-1-23+45*-6*-7-8*(9A+B)	B-A+9-(-876+54-3+21)
0813	01167	-1-(2+3-45-6)-(-789+A-B)	BA9-8-76+5+4-321
0814	01168	-12-34*5*(6-7)-8-9*A*-B	-B-(-A+9-876+54)+3-2-1
0815	01169	-123+4-5-(-6+78-9AB)	B-A9+8-7+6+5+43*-21
0816	01170	123+45+678-9+A-B	-B-A9+8-7*6*(-5-(4-3+21))
0817	01171	-12-(-3+4+56)-(-7-89A+B)	-B+A+9*8+765+(-4-3)*-2+1
0818	01172	-1+23+456+7*8*9*(-A+B)	-BA-9+876+5+43+21
0819	01173	-1-(2+3-4+5)-(-67-89A)-B	-BA+9+876-(-54-(3-2))-1
081A	01174	1+2-3-4+56+789-(-A+B)	BA9-8+7+65-432-1
081B	01175	123-45+678+9*A+B	BA9-8+76-(5+432)-1
0820	01176	-1-2-(-3-4-(-56+789+AB))	BA9+8-(7+65)-(-4+321)
0821	01177	-1+2+3+45-(-6-(789-A+B))	-B-A+9+876-5-43+2+1
0822	01178	1-2-3-4-56-7+89A-B	-B+A+98+76*5-(-432+1)
0823	01179	12+3+4+56+789-A-B	-B-(A+9)-(-876-(5*(-4-3)-2*-1))
0824	01180	-12-(34-5+6-7*8)+9*AB	B+A-(-98-765)-4-32*1
0825	01181	123-45+678+9A-B	BA-(987-6)+54*32*1
0826	01182	-12+3-45-6-(7-89A)-B	-BA+987+6-5-(43+21)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0827	01183	$-12+3+(-4+5)^* \cdot 6^*(-78-9A+B)$	$-BA-9+876-(-54-3)+21$
0828	01184	$1234-(567+8^*9-A+B)$	$B+A98-(7-(65+4-321))$
0829	01185	$-1+23+45-6-(-789-A+B)$	$B+A9-8-(-765+4)-(3+21)$
082A	01186	$-1^*2^*(345-678+9-AB)$	$BA-9-8+765+4-3-21$
082B	01187	$1+23-(-45-(-6+789))-(A-B)$	$-BA-(-987+6)-(54-3)-(2+1)$
0830	01188	$-1^*2^*3^*(-4+5)^* \cdot 6^*(7-(89-AB))$	$B+A-(9-876-5)-(-4-3^*-21)$
0831	01189	$-12-34-56-(-7+8+9A)^* \cdot B$	$B-(A-98-765-4^*3)-21$
0832	01190	$-12+345+6^*(-7+89)+AB$	$-B+A-(9-876+54-(-3+21))$
0833	01191	$-1+2-3-(45+6)-7+89A-B$	$BA-(-9-8)-(-765+43-2^*-1)$
0834	01192	$1234-5^* \cdot 67-89A+B$	$B+A-9+876-54+3-(2-1)$
0835	01193	$1-234-5+6-(-78-9AB)$	$B-A9+8^*765-4321$
0836	01194	$1234-5+6-7+8^*(-9A+B)$	$BA9+8-76+5^*4-321$
0837	01195	$-12+345+6-78^* \cdot 9-A^*B$	$B+A-9-8-7-65-43^*-21$
0838	01196	$1^* \cdot 2^*(-345+6+7-89-A-B)$	$-B+A+98-(-765+4-3)-(2+1)$
0839	01197	$-12+3+4^*5-(6-7)+8-9^*-AB$	$-B+A9-(8-765+4)+3^*2^*1$
083A	01198	$-1-(2+3-4)-(56-7-(89A-B))$	$-B+A-(-9+876)-54^*32^*-1$
083B	01199	$-1-(-2+3-4+5-(-67+89A)-B)$	$B+A98+76-5+4-321$
0840	01200	$123+45-6+789-AB$	$BA9-8^*(76-54+32)-1$
0841	01201	$-1-2-(-3-4-(-5-67+89A)-B)$	$-B+A-98-76+54^*(-3+21)$
0842	01202	$-1-(2-3^* \cdot 4+56+7)-8-9A^* \cdot B$	$BA9+87-6-(-5+432-1)$
0843	01203	$123-45+678-(-9A-B)$	$-B-A^*-98+76-54+3+21$
0844	01204	$-12+34-56+789+AB$	$BA-(9+8)-(-765+4+3-(2-1))$
0845	01205	$-123-4^* \cdot 56-789-(-A+B)$	$-B-(-A9-8-765+4)-3-(-2+1)$
0846	01206	$123-45-(-6-78+9^* \cdot A^*B)$	$-BA+987-65+43-21$
0847	01207	$1-(23-45+67-89A+B)$	$-B+A98+7+6^* \cdot 54+32+1$
0848	01208	$12-(3+45-6-789-AB)$	$-B+A+9-(-876+54)-3+21$
0849	01209	$1+2-34+56-7+8+9^*AB$	$-BA+987-(6+54)-3+21$
084A	01210	$1^*(-23-45+67)^*(8-9A)^*B$	$-B^*A^*(9-8+76-54+32^*-1)$
084B	01211	$12+3^*4-(-5-(-67+89A-B))$	$BA-(-9-(8+765+4))-(32-1)$
0850	01212	$-123-45-6+7+8+9AB$	$-BA+9+876+54+32+1$
0851	01213	$-1+2^*(345+6)-(-78-9-AB)$	$BA9+8+7+6-54-321$
0852	01214	$12+3-45+6-(-789-AB)$	$BA9+87+6-(-5+432-1)$
0853	01215	$-12+3-(-4-5-(-6+789))-A^*B$	$-B-A-(-98-765)-(4-32)+1$
0854	01216	$1^*2^*(-345+6-78+9^*AB)$	$BA-(9+8)-(-765-4)-(-3+2-1)$
0855	01217	$1-2+34-56-(-789-AB)$	$BA9-876-(-543+21)$
0856	01218	$1+2-34+5-(-6-789)+AB$	$B+A+9+8-76-5+43^*21$
0857	01219	$-1+2+34-(56-789)+AB$	$B+A-(-9-876)-(-5+43-(2+1))$
0858	01220	$-1+2-(-3-4-(-5-6))-(789-A^* \cdot B))$	$BA-9-8+765-(-4-3)+2+1$
0859	01221	$1-23+4+5-6+789+AB$	$-BA+987-65+4+32-1$
085A	01222	$-1-23-(-4+5)^* \cdot (-6-(789+AB))$	$-BA+987-6-(5-(4-3-21))$
085B	01223	$-1+23-45-(-6-(789+AB))$	$B+A-(9-876)-5-(43-21)$
0860	01224	$-123-45+6+7-(-8-9AB)$	$-B+A+987+6-5^* \cdot 4^*-3^*(2+1)$
0861	01225	$1+2+3-45+6+7-(-89A+B)$	$B+A+9+876+5-43-2+1$
0862	01226	$12-3^*(-456-78)-9^* \cdot A^*B$	$BA9-87+65-4-321$
0863	01227	$1+23-(45+6^* \cdot 7)-(8-9A)^*B$	$B-(A9-(876+54)-32)+1$
0864	01228	$12-34-56^*(7+89-AB)$	$B+A-9+876-54+32^*1$
0865	01229	$1+2+34-(56+7-89A)-B$	$B-A-9+876+5-(4+3^*2^*1)$
0866	01230	$1234-5+6-78^*9-A+B$	$-B+A-(-9-876)+5^* \cdot 4+3-(2+1)$
0867	01231	$-12+3-4+56-7+8-9^*-AB$	$BA9-876-5^*4^* \cdot 32^*1$
0868	01232	$12^*(3+4^* \cdot 5-(-67-(-89+AB)))$	$-BA+987+6-5-43+21$
0869	01233	$-1-2^*3-4^*(-5+6)-(-789-AB)$	$-B+A+98+765-4+32-1$
086A	01234	$1234+5-678+9A+B$	$BA9-8-7-6-(5-4+321)$
086B	01235	$1-2+3+45-67+89A-B$	$B-A+98+765-4-(-32+1)$
0870	01236	$123-45+6-(-789-(A-B))$	$B+A+9-(-8-765+4+3+2)+1$
0871	01237	$123-(-4-5-678+9^* \cdot A-B)$	$B-A+98+765-4+32+1$
0872	01238	$-1+2-34+5+6+7-(-89A+B)$	$-BA-(-987-6)-(54-32)+1$
0873	01239	$12+34+5^*(-6-(-7-(89+AB)))$	$BA9+87-6^*5^*4-321$
0874	01240	$-1^*(23-4-5-6+7-89A+B)$	$BA9-876+543+2^* \cdot 1$
0875	01241	$12-34-5+6-(-7-89A)-B$	$BA9-8+7+6-(-5^* \cdot 4+321)$
0876	01242	$-1-23+45-6+789+A^*B$	$-BA+987-6-(5^*(-4+3^*2)-1)$
0877	01243	$-1-(2-34)-(5-(-67-(8-9A^*B)))$	$BA9-876+543-(-2+1)$
0878	01244	$-12+3+45-67+89A+B$	$-B-A-9+8+7+65+4+321$
0879	01245	$1^*(2+3-4)^* \cdot 5+6+789+AB$	$B+A-(-9-876)-(-5+4-(-3-21))$
087A	01246	$1-(-23-4^* \cdot 5)-6-(-789-AB)$	$BA+9-(-8-765)+4-(-3-2+1)$
087B	01247	$1-23-4+5-(-6-(7+89A-B))$	$B+A-9+876-5+4-3-(2+1)$
0880	01248	$-12-3-4-56-78+9AB$	$-BA+9+876+54+3^*21$
0881	01249	$-1^*(-2-34-(-5+67-89A-B))$	$BA9-(-8+765)+432-1$
0882	01250	$12+3+45-67+89A-B$	$-B+A+98+765+43-2+1$
0883	01251	$-1-2^*3+4^*5-(6-789-AB)$	$BA9+8-76-5^*(43+21)$
0884	01252	$-1+234+567+89A+B$	$BA9-(8+76^*5)-(-4+3-2)^* \cdot -1$
0885	01253	$-12+3+45-67-(8+9A^* \cdot B)$	$-B-A-(-987+65+43-(2+1))$
0886	01254	$12+3-(-4+5+6+7)+8+9A^*B$	$-B-A^*-9^*8+7+65+4+321$
0887	01255	$1+2-3-(-4-5+6+7-89A+B)$	$BA9-8-7-6+5^*4-321$
0888	01256	$-12-3+4-56-(78-9AB)$	$-BA+987-(65-43)+21$
0889	01257	$-1-(23+4-(-5+6))-(-7-(89A+B))$	$-BA+9^*87-(-6-5-(4+321))$
088A	01258	$-1-23+4+5^*6-(7-89A+B)$	$-BA+987+6+5-4+3^* \cdot 2^*1$
088B	01259	$12-(34-5-6+7-89A)+B$	$-B-(-A9-876)-(54+32)+1$
0890	01260	$1^* \cdot 23-45-(67+8-9AB)$	$-BA9-(8+76+5^* \cdot 432-1)$
0891	01261	$1-(-2-3)-(-45+67-89A)+B$	$B-(-A+9-(-87+65)+43^* \cdot 21)$
0892	01262	$-1-2-34-56+7^* \cdot 8+9AB$	$BA-9+8+765-4^* \cdot 3^*(2+1)$
0893	01263	$-1-(23-4)-(5-6^*(7-8)+9A^* \cdot B)$	$BA-9+8+765-4^* \cdot 3+21$
0894	01264	$123+45-(6-7-89A)-B$	$BA9-8+76^* \cdot 5+4^*3-2-1$
0895	01265	$-123-4+5^*6^*(-78+9+AB)$	$-B+A+987+6-54-3^*21$
0896	01266	$1-(2+3+4+5^* \cdot 6-789-AB)$	$-B-A+987-(65-4)-(-32+1)$
0897	01267	$-12-(-34-5^* \cdot 6)-(-78-9^*AB)$	$BA9-876+543+21$
0898	01268	$12+34-5^*6+789+AB$	$-BA+987+6-5+4-3^* \cdot 2^*1$
0899	01269	$1-2-3+4-56-78+9AB$	$-B-(A-987+65+4+3+21)$
089A	01270	$123-4^*5+6+789^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A+987+(65+43)^*(-2+1)$
089B	01271	$-1-2-(-3-4-(-5+6))-(-7-89A)-B$	$-B+A-9-(-876-5)-(-4+32^*-1)$
08A0	01272	$-1^*2^*(-3+4)^*(567-8-9AB)$	$BA9+8-7+6-(-5-4+321)$
08A1	01273	$1-23+45-6-7+89A-B$	$B-A-(-987+65+43-(2-1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
08A2	01274	$12+3^*-4-5+6+78+9^*AB$	$B-A+9+876+5^*4+3-2+1$
08A3	01275	$-1-(23-45)-(-6-(789+AB))$	$-BA-(-987-6^*-5-43)-2-1$
08A4	01276	$12+34+5-6+789-A^*-B$	$BA98-7-6+543^*-21$
08A5	01277	$-12+3-45+6-78+9AB$	$-B-A+9+(-876-5-4-32)^*-1$
08A6	01278	$-12-(3+4)-(-5-6)+7+89A+B$	$BA9+87+65-432-1$
08A7	01279	$12-34-(56-7^*-8-9AB)$	$-B+A9+876-5-43-21$
08A8	01280	$-12-34+5-6-78+9AB$	$BA9-8^*-7^*6-543+2^*1$
08A9	01281	$123-4-56-7+8-9^*-AB$	$-BA+987-(-6^*-5-(43+2+1))$
08AA	01282	$12+3-4-56-78+9AB$	$B-A-9-(-876-5-4)+32+1$
08AB	01283	$1234-567-89+AB$	$-BA+987^*(6-5)-(-43+21)$
08B0	01284	$-1^*-2^*(345-67+89+AB)$	$-B-A+9+876+5+43-2^*1$
08B1	01285	$-1+2^*(-34+5)-(-67-8-9AB)$	$-B-A+9+876+5+43-2+1$
08B2	01286	$1234-5-6+7^*(8-9A)+B$	$-B-A-9+876-(5-(4+3^*21))$
08B3	01287	$1+2-34-56-(-78-9A^*B)$	$-B+A9+8765-(-43-21)$
08B4	01288	$-123+45-6-7-8+9AB$	$-BA-98+765+4+321$
08B5	01289	$-1+2-3-(-4-5+6)-(-7-(89A+B))$	$BA9+87-6-54-321$
08B6	01290	$-123-45+67+8+9AB$	$-B+A9+8+765+4-3^*-21$
08B7	01291	$12-3-4-5+6-7-8+9A^*B$	$BA+987+6+54^*(-3-2+1)$
08B8	01292	$123+4-(-5^*6+78)-9^*-AB$	$BA+9+8+765+43-2-1$
08B9	01293	$1-(-2-3-4-(5+6+7-(89+A)^*-B))$	$B+A9-8+765+43+21$
08BA	01294	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+789+AB$	$B+A-9-87+654+321$
08BB	01295	$1234-567+8-(-9-A)+B$	$B+A+987-65-43-(-2-1)$
0900	01296	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9A-B$	$-B-(-A+9-876-54-(3-2)+1)$
0901	01297	$-1+2+3+4-5-(-6-7)-(-89A-B)$	$-BA+987+65-4^*3-21$
0902	01298	$123+4-5-6+789-(-A-B)$	$B-A-9-(876+54)^*(-3+2^*1)$
0903	01299	$-1^*(2-345-678+9+AB)$	$-BA+987+6+54-3-21$
0904	01300	$-1+2+3+4-(5+6-7)+(89+A)^*B$	$BA+98+765-4-32-1$
0905	01301	$-123-(45-6-78-9AB)$	$B+A9+876-5-43-21$
0906	01302	$-1-2-3-(4-56-789-AB)$	$BA-9-(-8-765-43-21)$
0907	01303	$-1+2+3+4+5-(6+7-89A-B)$	$-B-A+987-(-6-(-5-43-21))$
0908	01304	$1+23-(45-(-6-78)-9AB)$	$B-A-(9-876-54-3-2-1)$
0909	01305	$1-(2+3)+4^*-5-(-6-(-78+9AB))$	$B-A+98+765-(43^*-2-1)$
090A	01306	$12+34^*5-(67+8)+9^*AB$	$BA-(-98-765)-(-4^*3+21)$
090B	01307	$-1-2-3+45-(-6+7-89A+B)$	$BA-9+876-54-3-2+1$
0910	01308	$-1+2-(-34-(-5+6))+7+89A-B$	$-BA-(-987-65)-(-43-21)$
0911	01309	$1-(-2-(-3+4-56))-(-7^*8-9AB)$	$B-(-A-9-(876+54-3^*2))-1$
0912	01310	$12-34-5+6-78+9AB$	$-BA9-87+6^*(54+321)$
0913	01311	$-1-(-23+4)-(-5+6)-(-7-89A-B)$	$BA9-8-(7-(6+54))-321$
0914	01312	$-1-2+3^*-45+67^*(8+9)+AB$	$B+A+9-87+654+321$
0915	01313	$-1-(2-(3-4^*-5^*(67-8)))-(-9A-B)$	$BA9-(8-7+6-54)-321$
0916	01314	$-1+23+4-5+6-78+9AB$	$-BA+987-6-(-54+3-2^*1)$
0917	01315	$12+345+678-(9+AB)$	$-BA+98+76+54^*(3+2)^*-1$
0918	01316	$1+23^*-4+5+6-7-8+9AB$	$BA9+8+7-6^*54-3-21$
0919	01317	$-12+3+4-5-6-78+9AB$	$BA+98-(-765+43-21)$
091A	01318	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9AB$	$-B+A9+876-(54+3)+21$
091B	01319	$1+2+3-(-45+6)-(-7-89A)-B$	$B+A9-8+765-43^*2^*-1$
0920	01320	$1^*234-(-56+7-8^*9A)-B$	$B^*A^*(-98+76-(-5+4-32)-1)$
0921	01321	$12-3+4+5-6^*-7+89A-B$	$-B-(-A-987)-65-(4-3)-(-2+1)$
0922	01322	$-1-23+4-56-7-8+9AB$	$BA+9-(-876-5)-43-21$
0923	01323	$1-23+4+5-67-8+9AB$	$B+A98+7+6+5^*-43+2^*-1$
0924	01324	$1-(23-4)-(56+7+8-9AB)$	$B+A9+876-(54-3-(2+1))$
0925	01325	$123-4+5+6+789-(A+B)$	$BA9-(8-(7-(-6-54+321))))$
0926	01326	$-1+23^*45+(6-7)^*(89+A-B)$	$-B-A+987+6-5^*4-32^*1$
0927	01327	$12+34^*-5-6+78+9AB$	$BA+9+876-54-3+2-1$
0928	01328	$123-(-4-56-(-78-9^*-AB))$	$-B+A98^*(7-6)-(54^*3+21)$
0929	01329	$-1+2-3-4-5-67-8+9AB$	$-B+A-9+876-5-43^*-2^*1$
092A	01330	$1234-567-8^*-9-A+B$	$-B+A9+876+5+4-32-1$
092B	01331	$1+234-(-5-6-(-7+8))+9^*-A^*-B$	$BA98-7^*-6-543^*21$
0930	01332	$-1^*(2-345-678-(-9A+B))$	$-B-A-(-987-(-6-5^*-4^*(-3+2-1)))$
0931	01333	$-1-2+3-4+5+6+7+8+9^*AB$	$-B-(-A9-876-(-54+32))-1$
0932	01334	$-1-2-(3-4)-(-5-6)^*7+89A-B$	$B+A+987-(-6+54)-(-3+21)$
0933	01335	$-1-2-3-4+5-67-8+9AB$	$-B+A-98-76+543^*2^*1$
0934	01336	$-1+2+3+4+5+(-6+7)^*89A+B$	$-B+A+9+8^*76-5+432-1$
0935	01337	$-1-2-3-4+5-67-8+9AB$	$BA+98-(-765+4)-3+2-1$
0936	01338	$1-(-2-3+45)-(-67-8)-9A^*-B$	$BA+9+876-5-43+2-1$
0937	01339	$12-3-4-(-56-7)-(-89A+B)$	$BA+98+765-4-3+2+1$
0938	01340	$12-3-4+5^*-6^*-78-9AB$	$-BA-(-987-65)+4+3-2+1$
0939	01341	$1-(-2+3)-4-(-5-(-67-(8-9AB)))$	$B-A+987-65-4-3+21$
093A	01342	$-1-(-23+45-67)-8+9A^*B$	$BA+9-876+54^*32+1$
093B	01343	$-1-(-23-4)-56-7-(-8+9A)^*-B$	$B-A-(9-8)-(76^*-5^*4+321)$
0940	01344	$-1-23+45+6+7+8-9A^*-B$	$-BA+987+6-(-5-43-21)$
0941	01345	$1+2+3+4-5-67-8+9AB$	$BA9-(-87-6)-(-5^*-4+321)$
0942	01346	$-1+23-(4+5-(-6-78))+9AB$	$BA-9-(-876-5)-(-4-32^*-1)$
0943	01347	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+89A-B$	$-B+A-(-98^*7+65-432+1)$
0944	01348	$12+3-45-6+78+9A^*B$	$BA+9+876+5-43+2-1$
0945	01349	$12+3^*(-456-78-9^*-AB)$	$BA+98+765+4-(-3+2)+1$
0946	01350	$1234-567-(8+9^*-A-B)$	$B-A-(987+6^*(-5+4-321))$
0947	01351	$123-4^*(-56+7-(89+AB))$	$B+A9+876-(5+4)-(-3+21)$
0948	01352	$1^*-2^*(-34+567-8-9AB)$	$BA+98-(-765-4^*3)-2-1$
0949	01353	$1+2-(34-5-67-8+9A^*-B)$	$-BA9+87^*-6^*-5+4-3-21$
094A	01354	$12-3-(-45-6)+78-9A^*-B$	$BA9-8+7-6^*-5^*-4^*3-2^*-1$
094B	01355	$12+3+4+5-6-78+9AB$	$-B+A+9^*(-8+76)-(-5-(432-1))$
0950	01356	$1-(23-45-(-6-78))+9AB$	$B+A-(-987-6)-54-(3+2+1)$
0951	01357	$1-23-45-6+7+8+9AB$	$-B-A+987-6-(5-(-4-3))-(2+1)$
0952	01358	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+89A-B$	$B-A+987-65-4-(-32-1)$
0953	01359	$1-2^*(-3-45)-(-6+7-89A+B)$	$B-A+9-(-876+5+4^*(-3-21))$
0954	01360	$1-(-23+4)-5-(-6+78-9AB)$	$B-A+987+6-5-4-32+1$
0955	01361	$-12-34-5-6+7-8+9AB$	$B+A-(-987+65+4-(-3+21))$
0956	01362	$-12+34-(5-6)-(78-9AB)$	$-BA9+876+5+4^*321$
0957	01363	$1^*2+3+45-67-8^*-9A+B$	$-B-(-A98+76+54-(-3-21))$
0958	01364	$-1-23^*-45+6^*(7-8-(9-A)-B)$	$-B+A9+8+765-4^*-32+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0959	01365	$-12-3+4*(-5-6)+7-8+9AB$	$-B-(-A9-876)+5-(-4-(-3-(2-1)))$
095A	01366	$1-(-23-(4+5))-(-6-78+9AB))$	$-B+A+987-6-54-32*-1$
095B	01367	$123-4-(56-7)-(-89A+B)$	$-B+A9-87+65+43*21$
0960	01368	$12-3-4+5-(67-(8+9AB))$	$BA+98-765*(-4+3)+21$
0961	01369	$-1-(23+4-56-(-78+9AB))$	$-B+A98-76-54-(-3+21)$
0962	01370	$-1*-2*(3-4)*(-567-(8-(-9+AB)))$	$B+A*9+876-5+4+3+21$
0963	01371	$1+2-3*(4+567-(89A-B))$	$-B-(-A-987+65-43)-(2-1)$
0964	01372	$12+34+56-7+89A-B$	$BA+9-(-876-5+43-21)$
0965	01373	$-1-(-234+56-789-(A-B))$	$BA9+8*-76+5*(43+21)$
0966	01374	$12+3-4-(-5+67)+8+9AB$	$B+A98-76-54-32-1$
0967	01375	$12-(34+5-(-6-7))-(-8-9AB)$	$B-(-A-987+65)-(-4-3)+21$
0968	01376	$1-(-2+3-45+6*-7-89A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9-876)-(-5+4*-32+1)$
0969	01377	$-12-3-(-45-6-(-78+9AB))$	$-B-A-(-987+65-43-21)$
096A	01378	$12-3-45-6+7-8+9AB$	$B-A-9+8-7+65+4321$
096B	01379	$-1-2*3-(45*-6-7-89*A-B)$	$BA+987-6*(54-32+1)$
0970	01380	$1+2+34-(-5+6*-7+8)-9A*-B$	$B-(-A-9+8+7)-(-654-321)$
0971	01381	$-123+456-7*(-8+9-AB)$	$-B+A98-76+5-4+3*-21$
0972	01382	$-1+2+3+456-7*-89-A+B$	$-B-A+987-6+5+4+3-2*1$
0973	01383	$123+4-56-7+89A+B$	$BA9+8+7-(-65*-4+32-1)$
0974	01384	$-1+2-(-3-4)-56+7+8+9AB$	$BA+9+876-5-4-3+2+1$
0975	01385	$1-23-4-5-6-(-7+8)+9AB$	$B-(-A98-7)-65-4*(3+21)$
0976	01386	$1-2-34+5-6-7-(-8-9AB)$	$-B-(-A9-876-(54+32*-1))$
0977	01387	$-1-23+4*5*(6-7)-(-8-9AB)$	$B-(-A98-7*(-65+43))+2*1$
0978	01388	$1+2+3+45-6-78+9AB$	$-B-A-(-987-(-6+5-4*-3))-(-2+1))$
0979	01389	$-12-3*-4*(5+6)+78+9*A*B$	$B+A9-87+65-43*-21$
097A	01390	$1+2-34-5+6+7-(-8-9AB)$	$-B-A9-8+765-4+321$
097B	01391	$-12+34+5-(-67-89A-B)$	$B-A+987-6-(5+4)-(-3-2)+1$
0980	01392	$1-(-23-4+56)-(-7+8-9AB)$	$B+A9+876+5+4+3+2*-1$
0981	01393	$-1+23-45-6+7-8+9AB$	$BA9+8*-7-6*(-5+43-2)*1$
0982	01394	$1-(-2-34)-5-(67-8-9AB)$	$BA9+87+6*-54-32*1$
0983	01395	$1+23-45-6+7-8+9AB$	$B+A9+876-5-4-3+21$
0984	01396	$-1+2-3+456-7*-89+A+B$	$B+A-(9+8-7-654)+321$
0985	01397	$-12+345+678-9-A-B$	$B+A+987-65+43+2+1$
0986	01398	$123-45+6-(7-89A-B)$	$B+A-9+8-7+65+4321$
0987	01399	$1234-5+(-67-8)*9+AB$	$-B-(-A98-7)-(-65+43+21)$
0988	01400	$-1+234-(5-678)-(9-AB)$	$-B-A+987-(6*-5+4)-3-(2-1)$
0989	01401	$1-2-34*5-6+7+89A+B$	$-B-A-(98-765)-(-4-321)$
098A	01402	$1+234-5-(-678-(-9+AB))$	$-B+A98-76-5-(43-2)+1$
098B	01403	$1-2*3*(-45-6)-(-7-8+9)*-AB$	$-B-A+987+65-43-2+1$
0990	01404	$-1-23+4*(-5+6)-7-(-8-9AB)$	$B-(-A-(98-7))-(-6-5+43*-21)$
0991	01405	$-1-(-2-345)-(67-8-9*A*B)$	$B-A+987+6-(5-4)-3+2+1$
0992	01406	$-1*(-23+45-(6-(-7+8)))-9AB)$	$-B-A9-(-8-765)-(-4-321)$
0993	01407	$123-45+6-7-8+9A*B$	$-B-A-9+876-54*-3+2+1$
0994	01408	$-12+34-(-5-6)-(7*8-9AB)$	$-B-A*-9*8-(-76+5)-432*-1$
0995	01409	$1+234-5+678+9A+B$	$-B-A-98+765+4+321$
0996	01410	$-123-4-(-56-78)+9AB$	$-BA+987+65+43+21$
0997	01411	$-1-(23+4-(-5+6)-(7+8+9AB))$	$B+A98-7+65*4-321$
0998	01412	$123-45+6-(-7-89A-B)$	$BA+9+876-(5+4)-(-3-21)$
0999	01413	$1-23-4-5+6+7+8+9AB$	$BA+9+876-5*4*(3-2)*-1$
099A	01414	$12+3-4+56-78+9AB$	$BA-(-98-765+4-3*21)$
099B	01415	$-12-(-345-678-9+A)-B$	$-B-A+987+6+5+43-21$
09A0	01416	$1-2+345+6-7+8*9A-B$	$B-(A+9)-87-(-6*-5*-43-(-2-1))$
09A1	01417	$-1+2+34-(56-7-8-9AB)$	$B-A9+(8-7+6-543*2)*-1$
09A2	01418	$12+34-5+67-(8+9A*-B)$	$B+A98-(76-(-5-43-2-1))$
09A3	01419	$-1-(-23-45)-(67-(-8+9AB))$	$-B+A98-76-54+3+21$
09A4	01420	$1+234-(5-678-9-AB)$	$-B+A98-7-65-4-32+1$
09A5	01421	$1-(-23-(45-67))-8+9AB$	$-BA-98*7*(-6-5)-4321$
09A6	01422	$1+234-(5-6)+789-A-B$	$B+A9-87+65+4321$
09A7	01423	$-1+23-4-(-56+78-9AB)$	$BA-(-987+65)-(-4+32-1)$
09A8	01424	$-1-2+345*6+7*-8-9AB$	$B+A-9*(-8-76)+54+321$
09A9	01425	$-1-23-4+5*6+(7-8)*-9AB$	$-B+A9-(-876-54)-(-3-2*-1)$
09AA	01426	$1-23-4+56+78+9A*B$	$-B-(-A98-7*(-6+54+3*-21))$
09AB	01427	$1*2-(-3-45)-(-6+7+8)-9A*-B$	$-B+A9+876-(-54-3*(2-1))$
09B0	01428	$-1-(-2-3+45)-(6-7*8-9AB)$	$BA+987-6-5+43*2*-1$
09B1	01429	$-1-23+4-56+78+9AB$	$-B+A*9*8*(-76+54+3+21)$
09B2	01430	$123+4-(-5-(6-(-789-AB)))$	$-B-A-(-987+6-54)-(-3-(-2-1))$
09B3	01431	$1-23+4-56+78+9AB$	$BA9-(-87-6*-54)-(-3-2)*1$
09B4	01432	$-12-(3+4+56)+78+9AB$	$BA-9+876+54+3*-2-1$
09B5	01433	$-1+2-34-5-(6-7*8)+9AB$	$BA+9-87+65+4321$
09B6	01434	$-1+2+345-(-678+9+A)+B$	$-B+A-(-987-6-5+4*-3*2-1)$
09B7	01435	$1-23-(45-67)-(-8-9AB)$	$BA+9+876+5*4-(3-21)$
09B8	01436	$123-4-56-78+9AB$	$B-A+987-(6-5-4*3-21)$
09B9	01437	$-12+34+5-6-7-(-8-9AB)$	$BA9-87-(6+54*3)+21$
09BA	01438	$123+4-5-6-7+89A+B$	$BA9+87+6*(-5+3-2*1)$
09BB	01439	$-1-(2+3)-(-45-(67-8+9AB))$	$B-(-A98+76+5-4+32-1)$
0A00	01440	$1-(-234-5)-(-6-(789+A)+B)$	$-BA-(98-765-432+1)$
0A01	01441	$12-3+45*6+789-(-A+B)$	$-BA-(-987+6)-54*-3-2*1$
0A02	01442	$-1-2+3-4*-5-6-7+8+9AB$	$B+A-(-987+6)-5-4-(-32+1)$
0A03	01443	$-1-2-3-(4+56)+78+9AB$	$-B-A+987-(6+5-(43+21))$
0A04	01444	$1+2-(-34-56)-78+9AB$	$-B+A98+76+54*-3+2-1$
0A05	01445	$12+3-4*-56-(7+8)-9*-AB$	$-B+A98+7-6-54-32+1$
0A06	01446	$12-3+4-(5+6-7)-(-8-9AB)$	$B+A9-(-876-54)+3-2-1$
0A07	01447	$-1-(-23-4-(56*7+8*9A+B))$	$B+A+987-(-65+43-2+1)$
0A08	01448	$123-45*-6-78*-9+AB$	$B+A98-76+5+4-32*1$
0A09	01449	$-12+34+5+6-7-8+9AB$	$-BA9+87-6-5*(-432+1)$
0A0A	01450	$123-(-4+5)-(-6+7-89A-B)$	$-B-A-(-9*-8*-7-654-32-1)$
0A0B	01451	$1+2+3-45+67-8+9AB$	$B+A+987-(6-5)+4+3+21$
0A10	01452	$-12-3+456+78*9-(-A+B)$	$-B+A9+876+54+3+21$
0A11	01453	$123+45+6+789+A*B$	$-B-(A+98)-(-76-5*4*3*21)$
0A12	01454	$12+3-456-7*(-8-9-A)*B$	$-B-A+987+6+54-3*-2*1$
0A13	01455	$-12+34-5+6-7+8+9AB$	$BA+987+6-54-3-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0A14	01456	$1 - (-2-345)+678 - (9-A-B)$	$-B - (-A-987+6-54+3) - (-2-1)$
0A15	01457	$12-3 - (45 - (-6-7+8*9*(A+B)))$	$-B+A+9+87 - (-6+5*4) - 3*2+1$
0A16	01458	$12-34-5* (-6-7) - 8+9AB$	$-B-A - (-987 - (-6+54-3+21))$
0A17	01459	$-12+345+6+789-AB$	$BA9-87*(6-5)+4*-32+1$
0A18	01460	$-1 - (-234-5) - (6-789) - (-A-B)$	$B - (-A98-7) - (65-4*-3+21)$
0A19	01461	$-1 - (2+345)+67 - (-8-9)*-A*-B$	$-B - (-A98-7*-6) - 5*4 - (-3+21)$
0A1A	01462	$1 - (2 - (34+5+6-7)) - (-8+9AB)$	$BA+987-65+4-3-(2+1)$
0A1B	01463	$1+23-4+5 - (-6+7-8-9AB)$	$-B-A+9+8*-7 - (-6+543)*-2+1$
0A20	01464	$1-2+345 - (-6-78)*(9-A+B)$	$BA+987-65+4-3-2+1$
0A21	01465	$123+45+6-7*-8-9*-AB$	$BA+987+65+43*(-2-1)$
0A22	01466	$1 - (-2-3+45) - (6 - (78+9AB))$	$-BA+9*-8 - (-7-65)*-4*(-3-2)*1$
0A23	01467	$-12-3*-4-5+67*(8+9)+AB$	$B+A98+76-54*3+2*1$
0A24	01468	$-1-2+345 - (-678-9-A)+B$	$B+A+987+6-5*-4-3+21$
0A25	01469	$12+34-5-6+7-8+9AB$	$BA9-8*-7 - (-6+5)*-4*3*21$
0A26	01470	$12+3-4+5*6+(7-8)*-9AB$	$B - (-A-987-6+5-43-2*-1)$
0A27	01471	$-1+23-45+67-8+9AB$	$B+A98+7-6+5+43*-2*1$
0A28	01472	$1+2 - (3 - (-45+6))+78+9AB$	$B+A+987+65 - (-4*-3*2+1)$
0A29	01473	$1+23 - (45 - (67-8))+9AB$	$B+A98+7+6+5-4*(3+21)$
0A2A	01474	$123-45 - (67-8)+9AB$	$B - (-A98+7) - (65+4+3+2*1)$
0A2B	01475	$12-345+678+9*-A*-B$	$B+A98-7-65-(4+3)-2+1$
0A30	01476	$-1-23-(4+5) - (6-78-9AB)$	$B+A98-76+5-4-3+2-1$
0A31	01477	$12 - (34-5-67) - (8-9AB)$	$-B+A98 - (-7+6) - (54-3*-2-1)$
0A32	01478	$-1 - (-2-3) - (4-56+7+8)+9AB$	$-B+A+987-6+54-3+21$
0A33	01479	$-12+34-56+78+9AB$	$BA+9+876+54-3+21$
0A34	01480	$-1-23+456-7*-89+AB$	$B+A - (-98+76*-5*4+321)$
0A35	01481	$-12-3+4+56*7+8*(9A+B)$	$B-A+987 - (65-4+3) - (-2-1)$
0A36	01482	$-1+2+34+5-6+7+8+9AB$	$BA9+8+7+6+5*-43 - (-2-1)$
0A37	01483	$-1 - (-23-4) - (56-78-9AB)$	$BA+987+6-54 - (-3+2) - 1$
0A38	01484	$-1-23+4-5-6+78+9AB$	$-B+A98+7-65-4*-3-(2+1)$
0A39	01485	$1+23+4-56 - (-78-9AB)$	$-BA - (98+76-5)+4*321$
0A3A	01486	$-1+23-45-6+78+9AB$	$-B+A98-76+5+43-21$
0A3B	01487	$-1+23 - (45 - (67+8+9AB))$	$-B-A+98+7+65+4+321$
0A40	01488	$-1* (-23+45-67-8-9AB)$	$-BA-9+8+76+543*2-1$
0A41	01489	$123+4-5+6 - (-7-8-9A*B)$	$BA+987-6-5-4-32+1$
0A42	01490	$-12-3+4+5+67-8+9AB$	$B+A+987-6+5-4-3*-21$
0A43	01491	$12 - (-34-5) - (-6 - (7 - (8-9AB)))$	$B-A+987-6-5-43*-2*1$
0A44	01492	$1-2+34 - (56-78-9AB)$	$BA9+8*7-6*-5+43-2+1$
0A45	01493	$1234-567+89+AB$	$-B+A98-76-5 - (-4-32-1)$
0A46	01494	$-1+2+34-56+78+9AB$	$-B - (-A98 - (-7-6) - 5+4) - 32-1$
0A47	01495	$-1 - (-2-345-6-789+A*B)$	$B-A+98+76*-5-4*-321$
0A48	01496	$12 - (-345+6) - (-789-A*-B)$	$-B+A - (-9 - (87+654))+321$
0A49	01497	$-1+2 - (-34-56-78)+9A*B$	$-B-A - (-987-65) - (-4+32*-1)$
0A4A	01498	$-1-2-3-4+56+7+8+9AB$	$B+A98-76-5+4-(3-21)$
0A4B	01499	$1+23+456-78*-9-(A-B)$	$-B+A98+7-65-4+3+21$
0A50	01500	$1 - (2-3)+4+56 - (7-8-9AB)$	$BA-9+8 - (-7-65+43*-21)$
0A51	01501	$-12+3*45-67 - (-8-9AB)$	$BA9-8 - (-7 - (6-54))*(3+2-1)$
0A52	01502	$-1+234 - (5+67 - (89A-B))$	$-BA+9+876 - (54-321)$
0A53	01503	$-1+2-3 - (-4*-5-6) - (-78-9AB)$	$-BA+9*(87+65)*(4-3)+21$
0A54	01504	$1-23+45-6-7*-8+9AB$	$B+A98+7-6-54-3+2+1$
0A55	01505	$-12-34*-5+6+7+8-9A*-B$	$-B+A98-7 - (6-5) - (4+3+21)$
0A56	01506	$-1+23-4* (-5+67)*(89+A*-B)$	$B+A98 - (76-5)+4*(3+2+1)$
0A57	01507	$12+34-56+78+9AB$	$-B+A98 - (7 - (-6-54+32))+1$
0A58	01508	$123 - (-4+5-67) - (-89A+B)$	$B-A - (-987-6-54)+32*1$
0A59	01509	$-1+2+3+456+7+8*(9A-B)$	$BA - (-987-6) - (5-4+32)+1$
0A5A	01510	$-1-2-3456-7*-89*A-B$	$B+A+987+65-4*3+21$
0A5B	01511	$123 - (-4+5-6) - (78-9AB)$	$-B+A98 - (7+6-5) - (4-3) - 21$
0A60	01512	$-12+3+4+5+67+8+9AB$	$B - (-A-987-6) - (-54 - (-3+21))$
0A61	01513	$-12+3 - (-4+5) - (-6-78)+9AB$	$B+A98-76+54 - (3+21)$
0A62	01514	$1-2*(3+45)*-6 - (-78+9)*A+B$	$-BA+98-7+6+543*2-1$
0A63	01515	$1+234-56-7+89A-B$	$B+A+987+65-4-3+21$
0A64	01516	$12+3 - (4-5-67 - (-8+9AB))$	$BA+987 - (6-5-4+3+21)$
0A65	01517	$-123 - (-456+7*-8) - 9*A*-B$	$B - (-A98+7-6-5+43+2+1)$
0A66	01518	$1+23-4+56-7+8+9AB$	$B+A+987+6 - (-54 - (3+21))$
0A67	01519	$-12 - (-34 - (-5+67-8) - 9AB)$	$BA9-87 - (-6-5)+43*2*-1$
0A68	01520	$1234+56*-7-89+A+B$	$B-A+987+65+4+32+1$
0A69	01521	$12+3-4+56+7+8+9AB$	$-BA - (9-8+(7+6)*54*(-3+2-1))$
0A6A	01522	$123-4-5+67+89A+B$	$B-A+987-6*5-4*32*-1$
0A6B	01523	$-1234+56*7*8-9A+B$	$-B - (-A98 - (7-6)) - (5-4) - (-3+21)$
0A70	01524	$1+23 - (-4 - (56+7)) - (-8-9AB)$	$BA+987+6-5+4+3-21$
0A71	01525	$-1+23-4+5+67-8+9AB$	$-B+A+9 - (-87-6) - 54*(3-21)$
0A72	01526	$1234-5 - (-67*-8 - (9A-B))$	$-B+A98-7+6*-5-4-3+21$
0A73	01527	$-1 - (-234-56-789 - (A+B))$	$-B - (-A98 - (7-65)) - (-43 - (2-1))$
0A74	01528	$1*2*(3+456-7+89+A+B)$	$-B - (-A+9) - 8 - (-765-4-321)$
0A75	01529	$-12+3 - (-456+78-9*A*B)$	$B - (-A-98) - (-7-654-321)$
0A76	01530	$-1 - (2+34)+5*6*7*8 - (9A-B)$	$B-A-9-8+765+4+321$
0A77	01531	$123-4-5+67-8-9A*-B$	$-B+A98 - (7-6)+5 - (-4-3+21)$
0A78	01532	$123-4-5*-6-78+9AB$	$-B+A9+87*6+543+21$
0A79	01533	$1-2+34+56-7+8+9AB$	$BA9-87-65+4-3-2+1$
0A7A	01534	$-1+234 - (-5+67) - (-89A-B)$	$-B+A98 - (-76+54) - (32-1)$
0A7B	01535	$-1*(2-3-4-5-(6+78)-9AB)$	$BA9 - (87+65+4) - (-3-2)+1$
0A80	01536	$1+23-4*-56+78+9AB$	$BA+987 - (6-5+4) - (3-2-1)$
0A81	01537	$1+2+34+56-7 - (-8-9AB)$	$BA9-87 - (6*-54+321)$
0A82	01538	$-1-23+45-6+78+9AB$	$BA9 - (87+65-4) - (-3+2)*1$
0A83	01539	$-1+23 - (-4 - (-5 - (-67-8)))+9AB$	$BA+987+6-5-4+3+2*-1$
0A84	01540	$-12+3+45+67-8+9AB$	$BA9-8+76-5*43*(2-1)$
0A85	01541	$-1-23-4+5*6*-7*-8 - (9A-B)$	$BA9-87 - (6+54-3+2*1)$
0A86	01542	$-1-2-34+56+78+9AB$	$BA - (-987-6) - (5-4) - (3+2-1)$
0A87	01543	$1+2 - (-345-67+8*(9-AB))$	$B+A98+7+6-5 - (4+3+21)$
0A88	01544	$-12 - (-34 - (5-6)) - (-78-9AB)$	$B+A98-76 - (54+3)*(2+1)$
0A89	01545	$-1*(2-3)*4*5+6+78+9AB$	$BA9-87+6+5-43-21$
0A8A	01546	$1*-2*(-345+6*(78-9-AB))$	$BA9-87 - (6+5) - (43-2*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0A8B	01547	123-(-456-7*89-A)-B	B+A98-7+6*5-4-32-1
0A90	01548	1+2*(34+56)-78+9AB	-B-(-A9+87)-(6*5*43-2)+1
0A91	01549	-1+2-3-4*5*(67+8)+9*(-A-B)	BA9-87-6-(54-3*(2+1))
0A92	01550	-123-4567+8*9*-AB	BA9-(87-6-5-4+3*21)
0A93	01551	-1-2+3+45+67-8+9AB	BA9-(87+6)-(5+43)+2+1
0A94	01552	123-45+6-7+8+9AB	B+A98+7*6-5-(43-(-2+1))
0A95	01553	-1-2-345*-6+7*-8+9A*-B	BA9-8-7-6-(54-3*-21)
0A96	01554	12-3*4*-5*6-7+8-9*-AB	-B-(-A98-76)-5-43-21
0A97	01555	-12-345+67*(-89+AB)	B+A98+76-54-32*1
0A98	01556	-12+34+5-(-6-(78+9AB))	BA+987-6-5+4-(3-21)
0A99	01557	-1+2345-(678+9AB)	-BA-(-9-876)-5-(4-321)
0A9A	01558	-1-23+4+56*7+8*(9+AB)	B+A98-76+5+43+21
0A9B	01559	1+2345-678-9AB	B+A98-(7+65)-(-43-21)
0AA0	01560	-1+2*(3456+7*-8*9*A)-B	BA9+8-(76-5)-43-21
0AA1	01561	-1+2+34*5+6-7*-8-9A*-B	BA9+8*(-76-5-(-43-21))
0AA2	01562	1*-23+4+56+78+9AB	BA9+8-(76+54+3)+2*-1
0AA3	01563	1-2*(34-(5+678-9-AB))	BA9+8-76-54-3-2+1
0AA4	01564	-1-23-(-4+5+67)-8*(9+A)*-B	BA9-87-6-(5-4)-32-1
0AA5	01565	123+45+6-(78-9AB)	-B+A9+876-5+4+321
0AA6	01566	1-(-2-345)+678-(9-AB)	BA9-87-(-6*5-4*3)-2*1
0AA7	01567	-1-(2-345-678-9A)+B	BA+987+6+5+4*3+2+1
0AA8	01568	123-4-5-6-(7+8-9AB)	BA9-8-76+5-43-2+1
0AA9	01569	1234+5+67*-8-(-9-AB)	B+A98-76+54+3+21
0AAA	01570	-1+2+3-(-45+6)-(-78-9AB)	BA9+87-6-5*(43-2-1)
0AAB	01571	-1+2+3+45+67-(-8-9AB)	B-(-A98-76)-54-(-3+21)
0AB0	01572	-1+234-(5-6)-(-789-AB)	BA9+8-(76+5)-43-2-1
0AB1	01573	1+23-4*-5+6+78+9AB	BA+987+6+54-32*1
0AB2	01574	1234-(-567+89A+B)	-B+A98-7+65-4-32+1
0AB3	01575	-1-2+345+6-(78-9*AB)	-B+A98-(-7-65-(-43-2-1))
0AB4	01576	-123+4-56*-7+89A+B	BA9+87+6-5*(43-2)-1
0AB5	01577	-1-(-23-45)-(-67+8)+9AB	-B+A98-(-7+6-5-43+21)
0AB6	01578	-1-2+345-(-678-9)+AB	-BA-98+(-7+654-3)*-2*-1
0AB7	01579	-12+345-67-(-8-9*AB)	B+A98-76+54-32*-1
0AB8	01580	1234-5-(-678+9AB)	BA9-87-(-6+54)+3+21
0AB9	01581	-1-2+3-4+56+78+9AB	-B+A-(98-765-432+1)
0ABA	01582	1+234-5+6-7+89A-B	B+A9+876+5-4+321
0ABB	01583	12-(-3-45+6)-(-78-9AB)	-B+A98-7+6-(-5+4+32*-1)
0B00	01584	12+3-(-45-67)-(-8-9AB)	-B-A9-(87+6-5)+4*321
0B01	01585	-123-(-456-789)-(A-B)	BA9-87*-6-543+21
0B02	01586	-1+234*5-67-89+AB	BA+987-(-6-5)-(-4+32*-1)
0B03	01587	-1-(-2+3-4-56-78-9AB)	BA9-(-8+7)-(-65+43-2+1)
0B04	01588	1-2+34-5*-6+78+9AB	BA-(-9-876)-(-54*3-2-1)
0B05	01589	1-23*(4+5-(-6+7))*-8-9-AB	BA9-87-6-5*4+3-2*-1
0B06	01590	-123-4*-567-(8+9AB)	BA9-(8+7+6+5+4+32*1)
0B07	01591	-12+345-(-6-789-(-A+B))	B+A-9*-8-7+6*5*43-21
0B08	01592	-1+23+45-6+78+9AB	-B+A98+76+5-43+2+1
0B09	01593	1+23+45-(-6+7)*8*-9*(A+B)	BA9+87-6-54*3-21
0B0A	01594	-1+2+3-(-456+7+8*-9A)+B	BA9+8-76-5-(4+3+21)
0B0B	01595	12-(-345-678-9-AB)	-B+A98+76-5+4-32-1
0B10	01596	-1-23+456+789-AB	BA9-8-7+6-5+43*-2-1
0B11	01597	12+345+6+789-A-B	-B+A98+76-(-5-(-4-32-1))
0B12	01598	1+234-(56+78-9AB)	B+A98+7*6+54-3*21
0B13	01599	-1-(-234-5*6)-7*8+9A*B	-B+A98+76-(54-3-21)
0B14	01600	1234-56*7+8+9A-B	BA9+8-76-5-43+21
0B15	01601	1+234-5+6+78-9*-AB	BA+987-(-6-5)-(-43-2*-1)
0B16	01602	-1-2+3+4-567*(8-(9-(A-B)))	-BA+987+6*54-32-1
0B17	01603	12+34+56-(-7*8-9AB)	BA+9+(-8-7+65+4)*(-3+21)
0B18	01604	-1+234+5+6+7+89A-B	BA9-87-6-5*(-4-(-3-2)-1)
0B19	01605	1+23*(4+56)+(-78-9A)*B	B-(-A+98-765-432)+1
0B1A	01606	12+3+4+56+78+9AB	-B+A9+87+654+321
0B1B	01607	-1+23-4+56+78+9AB	-B+A98-7+65-4-3-2+1
0B20	01608	123-4+5-6-(-7-8)+9AB	-B+A98+76-54+32-1
0B21	01609	-1+2-(-3-456)-7-8*(9-AB)	B+A98+76-5-4-32-1
0B22	01610	-12*(3-4-(56-78)-(-9+AB))	BA+987-(-6-54)-(3-2*1)
0B23	01611	-1-2-3*(-456+78-9A+B)	BA9-8+7-65+4-3-21
0B24	01612	-1-(-234-(5+6+7+89A)-B)	-B-(-A98-76+5-4)-(-3+21)
0B25	01613	1234-5-6*-78-9*A*B	B+A98-7-6-5*4*-3-2+1
0B26	01614	1+234+5+6-7+89A+B	-B+A98+(-7-(6+5+43))*(-2+1)
0B27	01615	-1-(-234-(-5-6))-(-7+8+9A*B))	B-(-A98-(76-(54+3)))+21
0B28	01616	-1+234-5+6+7+89A+B	B+A98-(76-54)+3*21
0B29	01617	12+345+6+789A-A-B	BA9-87-(6+5+4+3-21)
0B2A	01618	12+3+456-78*-9+AB	BA-(-98-76+5-43*21)
0B2B	01619	12+345-(-6-789A)+B	BA9-8-7-(-65-4*(-32-1))
0B30	01620	-1*23*4*(-5+6)*(78-9A+B)	B+A98+76+5-4+3+2+1
0B31	01621	1-234*-5+67+8-9A+B	B+A98-7+65+4*(-3-2+1)
0B32	01622	-1-2+34+56+78+9AB	B-(-A98-7-6-(54+3)+21)
0B33	01623	1+234-(-5-6-(-7-8))-9A*-B	-B-A+9+876-54+321
0B34	01624	1*-2*(-3-4-(-5-6-7*(-89A)))-B)	BA9-(-8+76+5+4-3+2-1)
0B35	01625	1+234+5-6+7-8+9A*B	B+A98-(-7-65-(-43+21))
0B36	01626	-1+234+5-(-6-7)-(-89A-B)	-B-A*-9-8+7+6+543*-2*-1
0B37	01627	12-3-45*-6+(7-8)*9A*-B	BA9-8+7*-6-54+3+21
0B38	01628	1-23*(4-5*(6+7))-89-AB	-B*(-A9+8+7*-6-5+4*(3+2))*1
0B39	01629	1*2-(-3-456)+789-AB	BA9+8-(76+5*-4-3)-21
0B3A	01630	1-(-2-3-456-789)-AB	BA9-8-(76-5-(-4+3))-2-1
0B3B	01631	123-(45+6)-(-78-9AB)	BA9-(87+6)-(-54+32)+1
0B40	01632	1-23-(-4-5*67-89A)-B	B+A98+76-(54-32-1)
0B41	01633	1*234-56+7*-8+9AB	-B-A+98-(-765-(-4+321))
0B42	01634	-12+3+456+789-A*B	BA9+8-(76-5+4-3+2-1)
0B43	01635	-1+2+3+456+7-8-9*A*-B	B-(-A98+7-(-6+5+43+21))
0B44	01636	12+345*6-(7+89A)-B	B+A98+76+5-43+21
0B45	01637	-12-3+45*(-67-8+9A)+B	BA9-87-(-65+43-2+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
0B46	01638	$12 * (-345 - 67 * 8 - (9 - (-A - B)))$	$BA9 + 8 - (7 + 6 + 54) - 3 - 2 - 1$
0B47	01639	$123 - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7 * 8 + 9AB$	$BA9 - (-8 + 76) - (-5 + 4 - 3 * 2 - 1)$
0B48	01640	$1 - 23 - 4 * 56 * 7 - 8 * 9 - A * B$	$BA - (-98 - 7 + (-6 + 54 - 3)) * -21$
0B49	01641	$12 + 3 + 456 + 789 - AB$	$BA - 98 + 76 + (54 - 3) * 21$
0B4A	01642	$-12 - 3 - (-4 - 567) + 8 * (9A - B)$	$BA9 - 8 - (-7 + 6) - 54 - (-3 + 2 + 1)$
0B4B	01643	$123 - 45 + 6 + 78 + 9AB$	$-B + A98 + 76 - 5 * 4 + 3 + 21$
0B50	01644	$-1 + 23 - (45 - (6 - 7 + 8 * (-9 - A)) * -B)$	$BA9 - (-8 + 76 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1)$
0B51	01645	$123 + 45 - 6 * (-7 + 8) + 9AB$	$B - A9 - (-876 - 54) + 321$
0B52	01646	$-1 * (-234 - 56 + 7 - (89A - B))$	$B + A98 + 76 - 5 - 4 - (3 - 2 + 1)$
0B53	01647	$1 - 234 - 5 - 6 * 78 + 9AB$	$B + A * 9 * 8 + 765 + 432 - 1$
0B54	01648	$1 + 23 * 45 + 67 + 8 + 9A + B$	$-B + A98 - 7 * (-6 - 5) - (-43 + 21)$
0B55	01649	$-12 - 345 - (67 - (8 + 9)) * AB$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 - 65 - (-4 - (-3 - 2)) - 1$
0B56	01650	$-1 + 23 + 456 + 789 - AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 * -6 + 5 + 4 - (-3 + 21)$
0B57	01651	$-12 - 34 - 5 * (-67 - (8 - 9A)) * -B$	$-BA - 9 - 87 + 65 - 4 * 321$
0B58	01652	$12 * (-34 - 5 - (-67 - 89 + A) - B)$	$BA9 + 8 - (-76 + 54 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
0B59	01653	$1 + 2 - 345 + 678 - 9 * -AB$	$B + A98 + 7 - 6 * -5 + (-43 + 2) * -1$
0B5A	01654	$12 + 3 * (456 - 78) - (9 - A + B)$	$BA9 + 8 - (-7 + 65) - (-4 + 3) - 2 * -1$
0B5B	01655	$1 + 2 + 3 * (4 + 56) - (-7 - (8 + 9AB))$	$BA9 - (-8 - 7 - 6 * 54 + 321)$
0B60	01656	$12 - 3 + 456 + 789 - A * B$	$-B + A9 - (8 - 765 - (4 + 321))$
0B61	01657	$-123 - 4 - 5 * 67 + (8 + 9) * AB$	$BA9 - (-8 - 7 + 65) - (-4 - 3) - (2 - 1)$
0B62	01658	$123 + 45 - (-6 + 7) - (-8 - 9AB)$	$B + A98 - 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 + 21$
0B63	01659	$123 - 4 - (-56 - 7 + 8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 87 + 6 - 5 + 43 - 2 - 1$
0B64	01660	$-1 + 2 - (-345 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 * -AB)$	$B + A98 - (-7 + 6 - 54) - (-3 - 21)$
0B65	01661	$1 + 2 + 345 - 6 + (-7 + 8) * -9 * -AB$	$BA9 - (87 - 65) - (43 - 21)$
0B66	01662	$12 + 3 + 456 + 789 - A * B$	$BA9 - (87 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 32 + 1)$
0B67	01663	$-1 - 23 + 4 * (-5 + 67 - 8) + 9AB$	$BA9 + 87 - 65 - 43 - 21$
0B68	01664	$1 + 234 - 5 - 67 - 8 + 9AB$	$-B - (-A9 - 8 - (765 - 4 + 321))$
0B69	01665	$-123 + 456 + 7 - (-8 + 9 * -AB)$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 - 43 + 2 - 1$
0B6A	01666	$-1 - 2 + 3 * (456 - 7) - 89 - AB$	$-B + A98 - (7 - 65) + 43 * (2 - 1)$
0B6B	01667	$123 + 4 + 56 - (-7 + 8) + 9AB$	$BA9 + 8 - 76 + 54 - 3 - 21$
0B70	01668	$1234 + 567 - 8 + 9 * -AB$	$BA + 987 + 65 + 43 - 2 + 1$
0B71	01669	$123 - (-4 - 56 + 7) - (-8 - 9AB)$	$-BA - (-9 + 87 - 65 + 4 * -321)$
0B72	01670	$-1 + 234 - (-5 - 67 - 89 + B)$	$B + A9 - (8 - 765) - (4 - 321)$
0B73	01671	$-1 * (-234 - 5 - (67 + 89A) + B)$	$-B + A98 + 76 + 54 - 3 - 21$
0B74	01672	$1 + 234 + 5 + 67 + 89A - B$	$BA - 9 * 87 - (6 + 5) - 432 * -1$
0B75	01673	$-1 * (-234 - 5 + 67 + 8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 87 + 6 + 5 + 43 - (-2 + 1)$
0B76	01674	$1 - (-234 - (5 - 67 - 8 + 9AB))$	$-BA + 98 + 765 + 432 + 1$
0B77	01675	$1 + 234 - (-5 - 6 + 78 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - (43 - 2) + 1$
0B78	01676	$-1 - (-234 - 56 + 7) - (8 + 9A * -B)$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 - 65 + 4 - (-32 + 1)$
0B79	01677	$-123 + 456 - (78 - 9A * B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 76 - (-54 + 3) + 2 - 1$
0B7A	01678	$-1 - 2 + (-3 - 4) * -5 - 6 + 7 * (89 + AB)$	$BA9 - 8 + 76 - 5 + 4 * (-3 - 21)$
0B7B	01679	$123 + 4 * 56 + 789 + AB$	$-B + A98 + 7 * 6 - (-54 - (3 + 21))$
0B80	01680	$1 - (-234 + 5 + 67) - (-8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 8 * (-7 + 6) * (-5 + 4 - 3) - 2 + 1$
0B81	01681	$-1 + 234 + 56 + 7 - (-89A - B)$	$BA + 9 - 8 + 765 - 4 + 321$
0B82	01682	$-1 - (-234 + 5) + 67 + 89A + B$	$BA9 + 8 * (-7 - (6 - 5)) - (4 - 32 + 1)$
0B83	01683	$12 + 345 + 6 - (-7 + 8 - 9 * AB)$	$B - (-A98 - 7) - (-65 - (4 - (-3 - 21)))$
0B84	01684	$1 + 234 - 5 + 67 + 89A + B$	$BA9 - 8 - (7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 * -2 - 1$
0B85	01685	$12 + 345 - (-6 + 7 - 8 - 9 * AB)$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 - (6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2))) - 1$
0B86	01686	$1 - 2 + 345 - 67 + 89A + B$	$BA9 - (8 + 7) - (-6 + 5 - 4 * 3 + 21)$
0B87	01687	$-1 + 234 - 56 + 7 - 8 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 87 + 6 - (5 - 43 - 21)$
0B88	01688	$-1 + 234 + 5 - 67 + 8 + 9AB$	$-B + A98 + 7 + 6 - 5 * (-43 + 21)$
0B89	01689	$-1 - (-234 + 56 + 7 - 8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 87 - (-65 - (4 - 3 + 2 - 1))$
0B8A	01690	$1 + 2 + 345 - (67 - 89A - B)$	$BA9 - (-8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4) - (32 + 1)$
0B8B	01691	$1 + 234 - 56 - 7 + 8 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 - (-6 + 54) + 32 - 1$
0B8C	01692	$-1 + 234 + 5 + 67 + 89A + B$	$BA + 987 - 6 + 5 + 4 * 32 * 1$
0B8D	01693	$-1 + 2 * (34 + 567) + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A98 + 7 + 65 + 4 + 32 * 1$
0B8E	01694	$-1 + 2 + 34 - 5 + 6 + 7 * (89 + AB)$	$BA9 - (87 + 6 * -5) + 43 + 2 + 1$
0B8F	01695	$123 + 4 - (5 - 6) - (-78 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 - (4 - 3) - 2 + 1$
0B90	01696	$-1 + 2345 + 6 * (-7 * 8 + 9 * A) * -B$	$BA9 + 8 + (7 - 6) * 54 + 32 + 1$
0B91	01697	$-12 + 3 - (-45 * 6 - (78 + 9A * B))$	$BA + 987 - (-65 - 4) - 3 * 21$
0B92	01698	$123 + 45 + 67 * (8 + 9) + AB$	$-B + A - (9 - 876 - 5) - (-4 - 321)$
0B93	01699	$-1 + 234 - (5 - 6 + 7 * 8) + 9AB$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 + 65 - 43 - 21$
0B94	01700	$1 + 2 + 345 + 6 - 78 + 9A * B$	$B + A98 - 7 * (6 - (54 - 32 - 1))$
0B95	01701	$12 - (-345 + 67) - (-89A - B)$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 * 3 * -2 * -1$
0B96	01702	$-12 - (-34 + 5 * -67 - 89A - B)$	$B + A - 9 - (8 - 765) - (-432 + 1)$
0B97	01703	$-1 - (-234 + 56) - (-7 - (8 + 9AB))$	$BA9 + 8 - (7 + 6) + 5 - 4 - (3 + 2) - 1$
0BA0	01704	$-12 - (3 + 4567 - 8 * 9 * AB)$	$BA9 + 87 - 65 - (-4 + 32) - 1$
0BA1	01705	$1 * 234 + 5 * 67 - 8 + 9 * A * B$	$-B + A9 * 8 - 76 + 54 + 3 + 2 + 1$
0BA2	01706	$-1 - 23 + 456 + 789 - A - B$	$-B + A98 - (-76 + 5 - 43 - 21)$
0BA3	01707	$1 + 2 * (-3 - 4 + 5 + 678 + 9 + A * -B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 76 - (-54 - 3) + 21$
0BA4	01708	$-12 * (34 - 5 - (-67 - (-89 - AB)))$	$BA9 + 87 - (6 + (-54 - 32)) * -1$
0BA5	01709	$1234 - 56 * 7 + 89 * (-A + B)$	$-B + A * (9 + 87 - 6 + 54 + 3 - 2 + 1)$
0BA6	01710	$-1 - 2 * (-3 - (-45 + 678)) - 9 * A - B$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 - 6 * 5 + 43 - 21$
0BA7	01711	$1 + 234 + 5 + 6 * 7 - (8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 * -6 - 54 - (-3 - 21)$
0BA8	01712	$-12 - (3 - 456 + 78 + 9 * -AB)$	$BA9 + 8 - 76 + 5 + 43 + 21$
0BA9	01713	$123 + 4 * (56 - 7) - (-8 - 9A * B)$	$BA9 - (-87 + 65 + 43 - 21)$
0BAA	01714	$1 + 2 + 34 + 56 + (7 + 8) * (9A - B)$	$-B - A + 987 - 65 * 4 + 3 + 21$
0BAB	01715	$-123 + 456 + 789 + AB$	$B + A98 - 7 - 6 + 5 - 4 * (-32 - 1)$
0BB0	01716	$-1 * 2 * (-34 + 56) * (-7 + 89 - AB)$	$-BA + 9 * 87 + 654 + 3 * (2 - 1)$
0BB1	01717	$1 - 2 * 3 * (45 - 6 * 7) * (-89 + AB)$	$-B + A98 + 7 + (6 - 54 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
0BB2	01718	$-1 + 2 + 3 - 4 + 56 + 7 * (89 + AB)$	$BA9 - (8 + 7) - (6 - 54) + 32 * -1$
0BB3	01719	$-1 - 2 + 34 + 5 * 6 + 7 * (89 + AB)$	$BA9 - 87 + 6 - (-54 - 32 - 1)$
0BB4	01720	$1 - 2 * 3 * 4 - 56 * 7 + 89 * (A + B)$	$B - (-A + 9) - (-876 - 5) - (-4 - 321)$
0BB5	01721	$1 - 23 * 4 * -5 - 67 + 89A - B$	$-BA + 987 + 6 + 5 - (4 - 321)$
0BB6	01722	$1 * (-2 - 34) * (56 - (-7 - 8) - (-9 + AB))$	$-B - A9 + 876 + 5 - (-432 - 1)$
0BB7	01723	$1 + 2 + 34 * 56 - 78 * (9 - A + B)$	$B + A98 + 76 + 54 + 3 - 2 + 1$
0BB8	01724	$-1 + 2 - (-345 + 6 - 789 - AB)$	$BA9 - (8 + 7) + 65 - 43 * (2 - 1)$
0BB9	01725	$-12 + 3 + 4 + 567 - 8 * -9A - B$	$BA9 - (8 + 7) - (-65 + 43 - 2 + 1)$
0BBA	01726	$-12 + 3 + 4 + 5 * 67 * 8 - 9AB$	$BA9 + 8 * 7 + 6 + 5 - 43 - 2 - 1$
0BBB	01727	$-1 - (2 - 345 * 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 * AB)$	$B + A98 + 76 + 54 + 3 + 2 + 1$
1000	01728	$-1 + 234 + 56 - 78 + 9AB$	$BA9 - (8 + 7) - (6 - 54) - (3 + 21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1001	01729	$1^* - 2 - 345^* - 6^* (-7+8) + 9^* - AB$	$BA9 - (-8+7-6-5-4+3-2-1)$
1002	01730	$1+234+56-78+9AB$	$BA9 - (87-65-(-4+32+1))$
1003	01731	$1-234+567 - (-89A+B)$	$BA9-8-(-7-(-6+54-32)) - 1$
1004	01732	$-1+2+345-6-7+89A-B$	$BA9+8-76+54+32-1$
1005	01733	$123+45^*6+789+AB$	$-B-A-9-(-876-54-321)$
1006	01734	$12+3+4^*-56^*-7-(8-9)^*-AB$	$BA9+8-76+54+32+1$
1007	01735	$-1-(-2+3-4+5^*67^*-8+9AB)$	$-BA-9^*-87+654-3+21$
1008	01736	$-1+2-(34-567)-8^*(9-AB)$	$BA9+87-(-6^*-5+43-2+1)$
1009	01737	$12-(-345+6)-(-789-AB)$	$BA9-8+76-54-(-3-(2+1))$
100A	01738	$123+45+67+8+9AB$	$B+A98+76+5+43+21$
100B	01739	$-12+3-4+5+6+(-78+9)^*(-A-B)$	$BA9+8-7-6+5+43-21$
1010	01740	$-1+2+3+4+567-8^*-9A-B$	$BA9-8+7+65-43+2^*1$
1011	01741	$1+234-(-5^*-6-7-8-9AB)$	$BA9-87+65+43+2+1$
1012	01742	$-1-(-234+5+6)-(-7+8-9AB)$	$B-(A+9+8-(7-65))-4^*-321$
1013	01743	$-12+3-(-456-(789+A)+B)$	$BA9+87-65+4-3+2+1$
1014	01744	$1-2-(-345+6-(7+89A-B))$	$B-A9+876+5+432+1$
1015	01745	$-123+456-7+89A+B$	$-B+A-9-87-(-6^*5+4^*-321)$
1016	01746	$1234-(-5+67)-89-AB$	$BA9+87-6-(54-3)-2-1$
1017	01747	$-12+3+4^*5+67^*(-8+9+A+B)$	$BA9+8+7+6-5-4-3+21$
1018	01748	$-1^*(23-4)^*(-5+6+7-89+A+B)$	$BA9+87-65+4-(-3+2^*-1)$
1019	01749	$1+23-4567-8^*-9^*AB$	$B^*(A9-8-7+65-4-3-21)$
101A	01750	$1^*2^*(34-5)^*(-67+89+A-B)$	$BA9+87-6-54-(-3-2+1)$
101B	01751	$1-2-3-4^*(-5-67)-8+9AB$	$BA9+8-(7-6)-(-5-43)-21$
1020	01752	$1^*-2^*(34+56-789+AB)$	$BA+9^*8+765-4+321$
1021	01753	$1+234^*5+6+7-8-(-9A+B)$	$-B+A9+876-54+321$
1022	01754	$-123-(-456+7+8)+9A^*B$	$BA9-8+7-6-5+43+2^*1$
1023	01755	$-12-345+678+9A^*B$	$-B+A+9-87+(-654+3)^*-2^*1$
1024	01756	$1-(2-(3+456+789))-(-A+B)$	$BA9-(-8-7-65+43-2^*1)$
1025	01757	$123+4-(-56^*7-8^*(9+AB))$	$-BA-(-9-8-76)-54^*(-3-21)$
1026	01758	$-1+234-5-6-(7+8+9AB)$	$BA9+8+76-5-43+2+1$
1027	01759	$-123+456-(-7-89A-B)$	$BA9-(8-76+54-3)+21$
1028	01760	$123+4+56-(-78-9AB)$	$BA9+87+6-(54-3+2-1)$
1029	01761	$1+2+3+456-789^*(A-B)$	$BA9-(-8+7+6)+5+43-(2+1)$
102A	01762	$1+23+456+789-A-B$	$BA9+8+76-(-5+43)-2-1$
102B	01763	$-1^*(-23-4-567-8^*9A+B)$	$BA9-87+65+43+21$
1030	01764	$-12^*(-3-4)^*(-56+78-9-A+B)$	$BA9+8+76-5-4+32^*-1$
1031	01765	$1+2-(-345-(-6-7-8)-9A^*B)$	$BA9+87-(6-5+43-2+1)$
1032	01766	$1+234+5+6+7-8+9AB$	$-B-A9-(-8+7-65)-4^*-321$
1033	01767	$-1+2+34-5-6^*-78+9^*AB$	$BA9-8+76+5+4-32+1$
1034	01768	$1-2-345+678-9A^*-B$	$BA9-(8+7)+6+54-(-3+2+1)$
1035	01769	$1234-5-67+8^*-9-AB$	$-BA-9+87-(6+5-4^*321)$
1036	01770	$123-4^*-56-(78-9AB)$	$BA9+8-7+6^*5-(-43+21)$
1037	01771	$-1^*(-234+5-(6+7-(-8-9AB)))$	$BA9-8-7-(6^*54-321)$
1038	01772	$123+456+7^*(8-(-9A-B))$	$-BA+987-(6-(54+321))$
1039	01773	$12+3+456+789-A+B$	$BA9+87-(6-5)-(4+32)^*1$
103A	01774	$-12-3^*4^*(-56-78+9)^*(-A+B)$	$BA9+8^*7-6^*5-(4-32)+1$
103B	01775	$123+456+7+8^*9A+B$	$-B+A98-76+54^*(3+2)^*1$
1040	01776	$-1-234+567+8-9A^*-B$	$BA9+87-6^*5-4^*3-2^*-1$
1041	01777	$1^*-234-(-567-8)-9A^*-B$	$BA9-8^*(7-6-5)^*(-4+3+2+1)$
1042	01778	$1-2+3+456+789+A+B$	$BA9-8-7-6+54-(3-21)$
1043	01779	$12+345+6-7+89A+B$	$BA9-8+7+65-4+3^*2^*-1$
1044	01780	$-12-(-34-567)+8^*9A+B$	$BA9+8+76-(5+43)+21$
1045	01781	$-1^*(-2-345-6-7-89A-B)$	$BA9+87-6-5+4^*(-3-2-1)$
1046	01782	$1+23+456-(-789-(A-B))$	$BA9-8+7+6+5+4+3-2-1$
1047	01783	$-12-3+4+5-6+7+(8+9)^*-A^*-B$	$BA9+87-(6-5)-(4+3)-21$
1048	01784	$1+23-(-456-789+A-B)$	$B-(A-987)+6^*54-(-3+2)-1$
1049	01785	$1-2+345+6^*7+89A-B$	$BA-9-(8-7-6+54)^*(-3-21)$
104A	01786	$1234-56-(78-9)-AB$	$BA9+8-(-76+54)+32+1$
104B	01787	$-1+23+4^*567-8-9AB$	$BA9+8-7-(-65+4)-(-3-(2+1))$
1050	01788	$12+3^*4^*5+6+789-AB$	$BA+98-7-6+54+3^*2+1$
1051	01789	$1+234-(5-67)-(-8+9A)^*-B$	$BA9+87-(6-(5-4+3-21))$
1052	01790	$1234-56-7+8^*-9-AB$	$BA9-8+76-5-4+3+2-1$
1053	01791	$1-2^*(-34-(567-8+9))-A^*-B$	$-B-A9+8+76+5+4^*321$
1054	01792	$-1-(23-456-7-(-8+9^*AB))$	$B+A9-(-87-6)-(-543^*-2-1)$
1055	01793	$12-(-3-456-789)-(-A-B)$	$BA9-8-(7+6)-(-54-32)-1$
1056	01794	$12-(3-4^*56)-(-78-9AB)$	$BA9-(-87-6)-(-5-4)-(-32-1)$
1057	01795	$123-(-456-789)-AB$	$-BA+987-(-65-4-321)$
1058	01796	$1-23+4^*-56^*-7-(-89+AB)$	$BA9+8-(-76-5^*-4-3^*2+1)$
1059	01797	$1-23+4-5-6-(7+8)^*(9-AB)$	$-B+A9+876+5^*-4+321$
105A	01798	$-1^*-2^*(3+4+567-8^*-9+A+B)$	$BA9-8+76+5+4-3-(2+1)$
105B	01799	$-123-4-(5+6^*-78)+9AB$	$BA9-8+76+5+4+3^*-2+1$
1060	01800	$-12+345-6-78+9AB$	$B+A-98^*-7-(-654-32)+1$
1061	01801	$1234-(56-(-78-9A)-B)$	$BA9-8-7+65+43-21$
1062	01802	$-1-234^*-5+67+89-A-B$	$B-(A9-8)-(-7-65-4^*321)$
1063	01803	$1-234-5-(-678-9^*AB)$	$BA9+87-6-5-(-4-3^*2^*-1)$
1064	01804	$1+23+456+789+A+B$	$BA-(-98-765)+4+321$
1065	01805	$1+23-4+567-8+9^*A^*B$	$-B+A98-(-7+6)^*5^*(43+2-1)$
1066	01806	$-123+456-78+9AB$	$B-(-A98-(-7-6))-(-5^*43+2)-1$
1067	01807	$1+2345-678-9^*AB$	$B+A+987-6-54+321$
1068	01808	$1-23-4-(-567-89^*A)-B$	$-B+A9-8+765+432-1$
1069	01809	$-12-(-3-456-(7-8))+9^*AB$	$BA9-(8-7+6-54-32-1)$
106A	01810	$123-4^*5^*-6+78+9AB$	$-B-(-A9+8)-(-765-432)+1$
106B	01811	$-1-2-(-345+6)-78+9AB$	$BA9+87-(-6-54)+3^*-21$
1070	01812	$-1^*(2-345+6-(-78+9AB))$	$BA9+8-(-76+5-4-3+2-1)$
1071	01813	$1-2+345-6-78+9AB$	$-B+A98+765+432-1$
1072	01814	$-1-23+4-(-567+89^*A)-B$	$BA9-8+76-5-4+3+21$
1073	01815	$-1-2^*(34+5+6-78^*9-AB)$	$BA9-(-8-7)-(-6-5)-(-43-21)$
1074	01816	$123-4-(-56^*7-8)+9^*AB$	$-B+A9-(-876+5)+4+321$
1075	01817	$-1-23+456-7+8-9A)^*-B$	$BA9-8-(-7+65-(-4-32)) - 1$
1076	01818	$-1+2^*-34^*-5^*(-6+7)-(8-9AB)$	$-B+A9+876+5-(-4-321)$
1077	01819	$1^*(2-3-45+67-8)^*(9A-B)$	$B-(A+9+876)-(-5^*432+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1078	01820	$1^* - 2^* (-3-4-567-89 - (A-B))$	$-B-A+987-6-5-4+321$
1079	01821	$1+234 - (-56-7) - (8-9AB)$	$BA9-8-7^*6 - (-5-43^*(2+1))$
107A	01822	$1-2+345+67+89A-B$	$BA9-8+76+54 - (32-1)$
107B	01823	$-12+3 - (4-567)+89^*A-B$	$BA9-8-7+65+43-2-1$
1080	01824	$1234-5-6-78-9A-B$	$BA-9-8+765-432^*-1$
1081	01825	$1^*(2+3)^*(-4-5^*-67+89-AB)$	$BA-98-76^*-5^*4-3+2^*1$
1082	01826	$-1 - (-2-345+67+8-9AB)$	$-B^*(A9+8+76+54-321)$
1083	01827	$-12 - (-345+67 - (8+9AB))$	$BA9-8-7 - (-65 - (43+2)+1)$
1084	01828	$12-3^*-456-7-89^*(-A+B)$	$BA9+87-6^*(-5+4) - (-3-2)+1$
1085	01829	$1+234^*5+6+7^*(-89+AB)$	$BA9+87 - (-6-5) - (4-3^*-2^*-1)$
1086	01830	$-1+234+5+67-8+9AB$	$B+A-9+876+54^*-3^*(-2-1)$
1087	01831	$-12+345+67 - (-89A-B)$	$BA9+87-6-5+43-21$
1088	01832	$1-2^*3^*-45-6 - (-78-9AB)$	$BA9-8+7+65+4+32+1$
1089	01833	$1234+5 - (6+7+89) - A^*B$	$BA9+87-6^*(-5-4) - 32+1$
108A	01834	$1^*(2+34 - (56+7-8-9))^* - AB$	$BA9 - (87+6-5^*43+21)$
108B	01835	$1234-5-67-8-9A-B$	$BA9 - (-87+6-54+32+1)$
1090	01836	$-12 - (-345+6-7^*-8-9AB)$	$B-A-9 - (-8-7-6+5) - 4^*-321$
1091	01837	$-1-23+456+789+A^*B$	$BA9 - (8-7-65-43+2+1)$
1092	01838	$-1-2+345-67+8+9AB$	$BA-9^*(-87-65)+43+21$
1093	01839	$12+345 - (67 - (-8+9AB))$	$BA9-8-7^*-6 - (-5+43)^*-2^*1$
1094	01840	$-12 - (-3+45^*(6-7)^*8-9AB)$	$BA9+87+65 - (43-2^*-1)$
1095	01841	$1234 - (-5 - (-6-78+9)) - AB$	$BA+98-7-6^*5^*(-43-2)^*1$
1096	01842	$-123+456+7^*-8+9AB$	$BA9+8 - (-76-5-43+21)$
1097	01843	$123-4-5^*-67 - (-89A-B)$	$BA9 - (-87-65+43-2+1)$
1098	01844	$1-2-3+456-78+9A^*B$	$BA-9+8^*-76+54^*32-1$
1099	01845	$1234 - (56 - (-7-8)) - (-9-AB)$	$BA9+8^*7 - (65-43^*(2+1))$
109A	01846	$1 - (-23-4) - 5^*-67 - (8-9AB)$	$BA+9+87^*-6+543^*(2+1)$
109B	01847	$-1+234 - (5-6) - (-78-9AB)$	$BA9 - (-87-6-54) - 32-1$
10A0	01848	$1+234 - (-5-67-8-9AB)$	$-B^*(-A+9)^*(8+7+65+43+21)$
10A1	01849	$1+234-5+6+78+9AB$	$-B-A+987+654-321$
10A2	01850	$123-4^*5^*(-6-7) - (8-9AB)$	$BA9+87+6-5 - (4-32+1)$
10A3	01851	$1234 - (5+67-8+9A) - B$	$BA9+8+76+5-4+32+1$
10A4	01852	$1+234^*5 - (-67+8 - (9+AB))$	$BA9+87 - (-6+5+4-32-1)$
10A5	01853	$1234+5+6-78+9-AB$	$B-A+987+(6-5)^*-4+321$
10A6	01854	$-12 - (-3 - (456+789) - A^*B)$	$-BA-9-8-7-65^*(-43+21)$
10A7	01855	$12+345-67+8+9AB$	$BA9+8-7^*-6+54+3+21$
10A8	01856	$1234+5-67-89-A-B$	$BA9 - (-8-7-65+43^*(-2+1))$
10A9	01857	$1+2+34 - (-5^*67+8-9AB)$	$BA9 - (8-76) - (-54 - (-3+2-1))$
10AA	01858	$-1 - (23-456-789-AB)$	$BA9+87-6-5+43+2^*1$
10AB	01859	$12+345+67+89A+B$	$BA9-8 - (-76-54 - (3-2-1))$
10B0	01860	$-1+23-4+567-89^*-A-B$	$B+A98+7+65^*4+3-21$
10B1	01861	$-1+2+3 - ((-4+5)^*6+7) - (-8-9)^*-A^*-B$	$-BA-987-6 - (5-432-1)$
10B2	01862	$-1-234^*-5 - (678+9^*-AB)$	$B - (A-987) - (-6+5-4-321)$
10B3	01863	$1234+5+6-7-8+9^*(-A-B)$	$BA9-8-7 - (6+5^*(4-32))+1$
10B4	01864	$-12-3+4-5^*6^*(-7-8)+9AB$	$B+A98-7+65^*4-3-2+1$
10B5	01865	$-1+23^*4-5-6^*-7^*8+9AB$	$BA9+87-6+5^*(4+3^*2+1)$
10B6	01866	$-1 - (23-456+7) - (-89A+B)$	$BA9-8+76-5 - (-43-21)$
10B7	01867	$1-2 - (-3-456)+789+A^*B$	$BA9+87+65-43+21$
10B8	01868	$1-23 - (-456+7-89A) - B$	$-B+A+9+876+5+432-1$
10B9	01869	$-12-3+456+789+AB$	$-B+A - (-987-654+321)$
10BA	01870	$-1-234-5 - (-6+7) - 89^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A - (-987-6-5 - (4+321))$
10BB	01871	$12-34+56^*7+8+9AB$	$-BA-987-6 - (-5-432-1)$
1100	01872	$-1+2^*(345-67) - 89^*-A+B$	$-BA-98-7 - (-65-4^*321)$
1101	01873	$1234+567+8+9A^*-B$	$BA9-8-7^*-6^*(5-4)^*(3+2-1)$
1102	01874	$12-3^*-4^*5^*(-6-78+9A+B)$	$BA9 - (-87+6-54-3+2+1)$
1103	01875	$1234-56 - (-7-8) - 9-AB$	$BA9+87+65+4+3-21$
1104	01876	$12^*(-3+4 - (-5-6)) - (-7-8-9A+B))$	$BA9+87-6+54 - (-3+2-1)$
1105	01877	$1234-56+7-8+9-AB$	$-BA+9+876+543-2-1$
1106	01878	$1234 - (56+78) - (9+A+B)$	$-BA9-8^*76^*-5-4-3-2^*1$
1107	01879	$1234 - (5 - (-67+8+9) - A^*-B)$	$BA9-8 - (-7+6) - (-5+4^*32^*-1)$
1108	01880	$-1 - (2 - (-3+456+789+AB))$	$B+A - (-9-876+5-432+1)$
1109	01881	$-123^*(-45-67-8+9A+B)$	$-B - (-A9-876-54-321)$
110A	01882	$1-2-3+456+789+AB$	$BA9+8+76-5+43+21$
110B	01883	$-123 - (-456+7) - 8+9AB$	$-BA-9-8^*-7^*-6^*(-5+4+3)^*(-2-1)$
1110	01884	$-12-345+678+9AB$	$B - (-A-987-6-5+4-321)$
1111	01885	$1234 - (5+67+8+9^*A-B)$	$B+A9-87-65^*4^*(-3-2-1)$
1112	01886	$1234-56+7+8-9A-B$	$BA9+87 - (-6-54)+3-2-1$
1113	01887	$-12-34-5 - (-678+9^*-A^*B)$	$-B+A^*-9+876+543-21$
1114	01888	$1 - (2-3) - (-456-789-AB)$	$BA9-8+76+5+4^*(-3+2+1)$
1115	01889	$1234 - (-56+7) - 89-AB$	$-B+A-9-87-65^*(-43+21)$
1116	01890	$-1+23+45-67^*-8-9^*-AB$	$BA9+87+6 - (-54-3-2+1)$
1117	01891	$1-234+567 - (8-9AB)$	$B+A+987+654-321$
1118	01892	$-1+2 - (3-456) - (7-89A+B)$	$BA9+8+76+5+43+21$
1119	01893	$12-34^*5+(67 - (8-9A))^*B$	$-B-A+987-6+54+321$
111A	01894	$1234-5+67-89-AB$	$B-A+9+876+543-2+1$
111B	01895	$-1-2 - (345-678)+9AB$	$BA9+87+65-4+3^*-2^*-1$
1120	01896	$12-3 - (-4-56^*7+8)+9AB$	$BA-9+876+54+321$
1121	01897	$1 - (2+345) - (-678-9AB)$	$-BA9+876+54^*(32-1)$
1122	01898	$1234+5-67-89+A+B$	$-B - (A9 - (876+543) - 21)$
1123	01899	$-1-2+34+5^*-67^*-8+9A^*-B$	$BA9 - (-87-65-4 - (3-2+1))$
1124	01900	$-1-2+345+6-7-8+9AB$	$BA - (987-65^*(4+32-1))$
1125	01901	$1234-56+7-89 - (-A+B)$	$BA9-8+76+5+43^*2-1$
1126	01902	$-1+234+5^*(67+89+AB)$	$BA9+8^*7-6+54-3^*-21$
1127	01903	$12 - (-3-456-789-AB)$	$B - (-A9 - (876+54) - 321)$
1128	01904	$1 - (2 - (345-6) - 7 - (-8+9AB))$	$-BA-98-7^*65^*-4+3^*-2^*-1$
1129	01905	$123+4^*-56^*-7+8 - (-9+AB)$	$-B-A+987+6+54+321$
112A	01906	$1234-56-7-8-9^*A+B$	$BA9+87 - (-65-4^*-3)+21$
112B	01907	$-12+345-6 - (-7-8-9AB)$	$BA9+8+76-5+43^*2-1$
1130	01908	$1234-56 - (-7-8+9A-B)$	$-B-A - (-987-65 - (-4+321))$
1131	01909	$-12 - (3+45+6^*-78-9AB)$	$-B-A+98-7^*-65-43^*-21$
1132	01910	$123-4-56^*-7+89A+B$	$B+A+9^*8^*7 - (-654-321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1133	01911	$1234+5+6*(-7-8-9+A-B)$	$B+A9-8-7-6-54*(-3-21)$
1134	01912	$12-345+678+9AB$	$BA9+8+7-(6+54*3+2*1)$
1135	01913	$1234-(5-(6-7))-(8-(-9A-B))$	$B-(-A98-76-5*43-2)-1$
1136	01914	$-1*-2*-3*(4-(56-78-9+A))*-B$	$BA+9+876-(-54-321)$
1137	01915	$1234-5-6+7-8-9A-B$	$B+A-9*-87-(-654-32-1)$
1138	01916	$1234-5+6+7-(8-(-9-AB))$	$BA-9-8-(7+6*5)-4*-321$
1139	01917	$1*-2+3-(-456+7)-(-89A-B)$	$BA9+8+7-6-54*-3-(-2-1)$
113A	01918	$1234+56-78-(-9+AB)$	$BA9+87+65+(4-3)*21$
113B	01919	$-12-(-345-6-7-8)+9AB$	$BA9-(87-65*4-3-2*-1)$
1140	01920	$1*(-2-3)*4*(-56-(-78-(9-AB)))$	$BA9-(8+76-5)+4*-3*-21$
1141	01921	$1*-2-3-(45-6*78-9AB)$	$B+A98-(-7-6*54+32-1)$
1142	01922	$1+23+456-7+89A-B$	$-B+A98-7-65+4+321$
1143	01923	$-12-(-34+56*-7-(8+9AB))$	$B-A-9+8+76+5+4*321$
1144	01924	$1+2+3+45-6+7+8+9AB$	$B-A-9+87-(-6+5-4*321)$
1145	01925	$12+3+456+7+89A-B$	$BA9+87+6+5+4+32+1$
1146	01926	$1-2-3+456+7+89A+B$	$BA9-(-87-65)-(-4-32+1)$
1147	01927	$-12+3*(-4+567-(8+9)-AB)$	$BA+987+6-5*(-43-21)$
1148	01928	$1*(-2+3)*4*(-567+89A+B)$	$-B+A+987+65-4+321$
1149	01929	$123+4+567+8*9A+B$	$-BA9-8*-76*5+4-32*-1$
114A	01930	$-12-3-4+5+6+7+8+9*-A*-B$	$BA9-8+7-(65+4)*3-21$
114B	01931	$1234-(5+6)+7-(-8-(-9A-B))$	$-B+A*9+876-5+432+1$
1150	01932	$1234-5+6-(-7-8)-9-AB$	$-B-(A-987+6)-5*-4*(3+21)$
1151	01933	$12+3-(-456+7)-(-89A-B)$	$B+A98-76-5+4+321$
1152	01934	$1234-56-7+8*9-AB$	$BA9-8+76+5+4-3*-21$
1153	01935	$12-(-345+6-7-8-9AB)$	$BA9+87-(-65-4)+32*1$
1154	01936	$-12+3*(456+7-8+9)*(-A+B)$	$-B+A98+7-65-(-4-321)$
1155	01937	$-1+23+4+5*6*7-8*9*(-A-B)$	$B-(-A98-(-7-6*(-54-3)))+21$
1156	01938	$1234-56-(78-(9A+B))$	$B-A+987-65+432+1$
1157	01939	$1234-5-6-7+8-9A+B$	$-BA9+8*76*5+4+3-2-1$
1158	01940	$-1-234-56*-7*8-9AB$	$BA+987+6-5+4+321$
1159	01941	$1+23+456+78-9*-AB$	$BA9+87+65+4+3-(2+1)$
115A	01942	$123-4+567-8*(9-AB)$	$BA9+87+65+4+3-2*1$
115B	01943	$1-2-3+4+5-(-6*78-9AB)$	$B-(-A98+76-5)+4+321$
1160	01944	$1+23+456-(7-89A)+B$	$-B-A*-98-7+6-(-543-21)$
1161	01945	$-1*(-2-3+4+5+6*(-7-89-AB))$	$-B-(-A98+76*5)-(-43-2+1)$
1162	01946	$1234-5-(-67-89+AB)$	$BA9-87+6*(-5-43)*(-2+1)$
1163	01947	$-123-456-78*(-9-A-B)$	$B-(-A-987+6+5+4+321))$
1164	01948	$1-23+4+567-8+9*AB$	$B-A*(-98+7-65-4)+32-1$
1165	01949	$-1-23-(-456+78)+9AB$	$-BA-(-987-65-432)+1$
1166	01950	$-1-2*(34-(-5+678))+9A+B$	$B+A98+7-65-4+321$
1167	01951	$1-234+56+7+89*(A+B)$	$BA-9*(-87-6-54-3-21)$
1168	01952	$1234-56+78-9-AB$	$-B+A98+7*(-6+54)-(-3-2*-1)$
1169	01953	$1234+5-(-6-(7+8-9A)+B)$	$BA+9+876+5*4*(-3-21)$
116A	01954	$1234+56-7*8+9-AB$	$B+A98-(76+5*4)+321$
116B	01955	$1234-56-7-8-9-(A+B)$	$BA9-87+65*4+32-1$
1170	01956	$-1+23+456+7+89A+B$	$B+A98-76+5+4+32-1$
1171	01957	$12+3+4-(5-6-(7+8))*(9A+B)$	$BA+98-(-765+432*-1)$
1172	01958	$12-(34-5)+6*78+9AB$	$-B-A-(9-(876+543)+21)$
1173	01959	$1234+5+67-(-8-9*(-A-B))$	$B+A-(-9+8*7*6)+5*(-4+321)$
1174	01960	$12-34+567+8+9*AB$	$-BA9+876-54*32-1$
1175	01961	$1234-5-6-(78-9)-(-A+B)$	$-B+A98+7*-6+5-(-4-321)$
1176	01962	$1234+5*(6-7+8)-9A-B$	$B+A*9-(-876-5+432*-1)$
1177	01963	$1+23+45-6*78-9AB$	$B-(-A9+876-5*(432-1))$
1178	01964	$1*-2*(3*4-5-6)*(-789+AB)$	$BA9-(87-6*(54-3-2)*1)$
1179	01965	$1234-5+6-(-7-8+9A-B)$	$BA9+87+65*-4+321$
117A	01966	$1-23-(4+5)*67-(-89A-B)$	$BA9-87-(-6*54+3)-21$
117B	01967	$1234+5-(-6+78)-9-A+B$	$-B-A*-987+65*4*(-32-1)$
1180	01968	$1234-5-(6-7+89-A-B)$	$BA9+87+(6-5)*4*32*1$
1181	01969	$1234+5+6+7+89*(A-B)$	$-B-(-A98-76*5)-43+21$
1182	01970	$1234-56-(-78-(9-AB))$	$-B-A+98+76*5*4+3*21$
1183	01971	$12+3+4-5*(-6-78)+9AB$	$BA9-876-5*-4*3*21$
1184	01972	$1234-5-(67-8)-(9+A)+B$	$BA9+87+65+4-3*-21$
1185	01973	$-1-23-45-67*(89-AB)$	$B+A98-7*6-5-4+321$
1186	01974	$-12*-3*(-45-6+7-(8-(9A-B)))$	$-BA9-(-8-(-7+65))*(-4+32)-1$
1187	01975	$-1+2-3-(-456+78-9AB)$	$-B-A9*(-8-7)-(-65-(-43+21))$
1188	01976	$1234-5-67-(8-(-9-(-A-B)))$	$-B-A-(-9-876-543)-21$
1189	01977	$1-(-2-(-3+456)+78-9AB)$	$BA9-(-87+6)+54*3-21$
118A	01978	$1234+5-6+7-89+A+B$	$BA-9-(-8-76*5*4)+32-1$
118B	01979	$1234-5-6+7-8*9A+B$	$B-A-9-8-7-65*(-4-(-3+21))$
1190	01980	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7-8+9AB$	$B-A-9+876+543-21$
1191	01981	$-1+2+3+4+56-(78-9AB)$	$-B-A+987-6-5+4+32*1$
1192	01982	$12+3*-4*56+78*(9+A+B)$	$B+A98-(7*6*(-5+4)-321)$
1193	01983	$12+3-4-(-56+78)-9*-AB$	$-B+A-(-987+6*5-432)+1$
1194	01984	$-12+3+45-6+78+9AB$	$BA+987+6-5*4+321$
1195	01985	$-12-(-345-67-(8+9AB))$	$BA-9+876-5+4+32+1$
1196	01986	$-12+3+4+5+6*-7*-8-9*-AB$	$-B-(A+9)-(-876-543-(2+1))$
1197	01987	$1234-56+7-(8-9)-(A+B)$	$B+A9-87-(65-(-4+3))*-21$
1198	01988	$12-(-345-6)-(-7*-8-9AB)$	$BA*(987-654-321)$
1199	01989	$12-3+4-(5-(6*78+9AB))$	$BA9+87-(-6+54*3+21)$
119A	01990	$-123-(-456-78)+9AB$	$-B+A98-7-6+5-4+321$
119B	01991	$-12+3*456+(-7+8)*-9*-A-B$	$B*(-A+9+87-(-65-4)-(-3-2+1))$
11A0	01992	$1234-5-6+7+8-9+A+B$	$-B-(A-987)+6-5+4+32-1$
11A1	01993	$-12-34-(5+6-(-7+89))*(A+B)$	$BA+987-(6-5+4-321)$
11A2	01994	$12+3+4+56-7+8+9AB$	$BA9+87-65+4*321$
11A3	01995	$1234-56-7-8+9-A+B$	$-BA-9-(-8+765-4)*(-3+2-1)$
11A4	01996	$-12-(-345-6-78-9AB)$	$-B+A+9+876+543-21$
11A5	01997	$12+3+4+5+6+7-8+9AB$	$-BA+987-6-(-543+21)$
11A6	01998	$1234-(5+67)-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A98-76*-5+4*(3-2)-1$
11A7	01999	$1-2-(-345-6*7*8-9*AB)$	$BA9-8-76+54*3*2*-1$
11A8	02000	$1234-5-6-(-7*8-9*-A+B)$	$B+A-(9-(876-(-543+21)))$
11A9	02001	$1+2-(-345+6-78)+9AB$	$-B+A-9+876+543+2*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
11AA	02002	$-12*(-34-(-5-6-7-8+9A+B))$	$-B-A+987+6+5-(-432+1)$
11AB	02003	$-1+234+5*67-(-89A-B)$	$BA+9+876-5+432+1$
11B0	02004	$-12-34+567+89A-B$	$-B-(A-9-876)-(-543-(2+1))$
11B1	02005	$1+234+5*67+89A+B$	$BA9+8+76-54*3+2*1$
11B2	02006	$1-23+456+78-9A*-B$	$-BA-98-7+6-5*(4-321)$
11B3	02007	$1234-56+7-8+9A-A-B$	$-BA-9*87+6+5*432*1$
11B4	02008	$1-2-(-3-(-45-67*8))+9AB$	$B-A-(9-876-543)-(-2-1)$
11B5	02009	$1234-56+7-8+9-A+B$	$-B+A98-7+654-321$
11B6	02010	$1234-5-(67-8-9-A)+B$	$B+A98-7-6-5+4+321$
11B7	02011	$1234-56-(-7+8)-9-(-A-B)$	$BA9-(8+7)+65*4-(-3-2)*1$
11B8	02012	$12+345-6+78+9AB$	$BA+987+654-321$
11B9	02013	$-1+2*(-3-45+678+9A-B)$	$B-A+9-(-8+7-65*(43-21))$
11BA	02014	$-1*(-2+34)*(5+67-8-9A-B)$	$B-A+987-6+5+432+1$
11BB	02015	$-1-2-(34-567-89A+B)$	$-B+A98+765-432-1$
1200	02016	$-12*-3*(-45+67-8+9+A+B)$	$-B+A98+765+432*-1$
1201	02017	$1+2+345-(-6-7-8-9A)*B$	$-B-(-A98-765+432-1)$
1202	02018	$1234-(-5+6-78+9A+B)$	$BA9+8-7-65*-4-3-2+1$
1203	02019	$1234+5+67+8-9A-B$	$BA9+8-76*5-4*32*-1$
1204	02020	$1234+56-7+89*(A-B)$	$B+A98-7-6+5-(-4-321)$
1205	02021	$1234+56-7-(89+A)+B$	$-B-A9-8-765*(-4+3)*2-1$
1206	02022	$1234+5-(6-(-7+89-AB))$	$-BA+987-6-543*(-2+1)$
1207	02023	$-1+23-4+56+7(8)*9(A+B)$	$-B-(-A98-7)+654-321$
1208	02024	$1234+56-(-7+8)-9(A-B)$	$B+A98+7-6-5+4+321$
1209	02025	$1234+5+67-8-9A+B$	$B-A9-8-7*65*-4-3+2*-1$
120A	02026	$1234-56+7+8*(-9+A)+B$	$B+A98+7-6+5-(-4-321)$
120B	02027	$-1+2+34-(-567-8-9*A+B)$	$-B+A98-(-76*5-4-3)+21$
1210	02028	$-12-3-4-5+67*(-89+AB)$	$-B-(-A98-76)-(-54-321)$
1211	02029	$12-3*(-456+78-9A)+B$	$-B+A98+7*(6+54)-3-2-1$
1212	02030	$1*-2*(3-4-(567+89))+A*-B$	$B+A9-8-7+65+4*321$
1213	02031	$1234-5+67+8-9A+B$	$B-(-A98+7+6)-(-5*4-321)$
1214	02032	$1234+5-6-7-8-9-A+B$	$BA9-87-6*54-32*-1$
1215	02033	$1234-56+7-89+AB$	$B+A+987+(6-5)*432-1$
1216	02034	$-1-23+4+567+89A-B$	$-BA9-87+65*(43-(2-1))$
1217	02035	$1234+5*-6-78-9-A*-B$	$-B*(-A9-8-76+54+3-21)$
1218	02036	$1234-(5-(-6-7+8-9A))*-B$	$B+A98-7*(-6*5-4*3-21)$
1219	02037	$-12-3-4+567+89A-B$	$B+A98+765-432-1$
121A	02038	$1234-5+6+7+89-AB$	$B+A98-(-765+432*1)$
121B	02039	$1+2-(-34*56+7*89)+AB$	$B-(-A9+87-65*(43-21))$
1220	02040	$12+34+567+8+9*AB$	$B+A+9+876+543-2-1$
1221	02041	$-1-(-2+34-567)+89A+B$	$BA9-8*7-65-(-4-321)$
1222	02042	$1234-5+6+78-9A+B$	$-B-(-A98+7+6+5*-43*-2*-1)$
1223	02043	$1234+5-6-7*(-8-9)-AB$	$B+A98-76*5+43-21$
1224	02044	$-12+3-4+5-67*(89-AB)$	$B+A9-8*7+65*-4*3*2*-1$
1225	02045	$1234-(5-6)-7-(-89-A*-B)$	$B+A98-(-7-654+321)$
1226	02046	$-1*2*3*(456-7+8*(9-AB))$	$B+A9+8-7+65-4*321$
1227	02047	$1234-5-(6-7)+89+A*-B$	$-BA-(-987+6-543)+21$
1228	02048	$123+456-7*-8+9*AB$	$B-A-(-9-876)+543+21$
1229	02049	$1234+56-78+9*(-A+B)$	$BA9-(-87-65+4*(-32-1))$
122A	02050	$-1*(234+5-678-9AB)$	$B-(-A98-76)-(-54-321)$
122B	02051	$-12-(-3-4-567-89A+B)$	$BA9+87*6+5*43-21$
1230	02052	$-12+3*4-5+67*8+9AB$	$BA+9+87-(-6+54*(-3-21))$
1231	02053	$-12-3+456-7+8+9AB$	$BA-(9-8)-(-7-65)-4*-321$
1232	02054	$12-34+567+89A+B$	$-B+A98-(7-6)*5*43*2-1$
1233	02055	$1234+56+7-89A+B$	$-BA9-8*(765-432)*-1$
1234	02056	$-1-23*(-4-5-6)-7*(-89-AB)$	$B+A98+7*(65-4)+3-21$
1235	02057	$-12+3+456+7-8+9AB$	$BA-(-9+8*7)-(-654+3)*-2*-1$
1236	02058	$-1-(-2-(3-4))-(-567-89A)-B$	$BA9+8-(7+6)*(-54+32)-1$
1237	02059	$1-23-4+567-8-9A*-B$	$-BA+987-(-6-(543+21))$
1238	02060	$1-(-2-3+4-567-89A+B)$	$BA9-87-6-5+4+321$
1239	02061	$-1-2*-345-67-8-9*-AB$	$-BA9+8+7*(-65+432+1)$
123A	02062	$1234-56+78-9-A-B$	$BA9-(87+6-5-(-4+321))$
123B	02063	$1234-(5-6)-(-7*(-8+9))-A)-B$	$BA9-(8+76+5+4-321)$
1240	02064	$1234-56-7+8*9+A-B$	$BA9-87-(-6-(-5-4+321))$
1241	02065	$1234-(5-(-67+8*9))-A)+B$	$BA-9*-876-(5432+1)$
1242	02066	$1234-5+6+7*(8+9)+A*-B$	$BA9+87-6+5*43-(-2+1)$
1243	02067	$-123-(-4-567-8)+9AB$	$BA9+87-6+5*43+2*1$
1244	02068	$-1-2+3+456-(-7+8-9AB)$	$BA+987+6+54+321$
1245	02069	$1234+5+67+8+9*-A+B$	$-B-A+987+65-432*-1$
1246	02070	$1234+56-(78-9)-(-A-B)$	$-B-A+987+65+432+1$
1247	02071	$12-(-3-456-(-7-8)-9AB)$	$B+A98+76*5+43+2+1$
1248	02072	$-12*(-3-4+5)*(67+89-A*B)$	$B-(-A9-87-6)-5+4*321$
1249	02073	$12-3-45-6+(78+9)*(A+B)$	$BA9-8-(76-5)-(-4-321)$
124A	02074	$-1+2-(3+4)+567-(-89A-B)$	$-B+A98-76+5-432*-1$
124B	02075	$1234+5-67-8-9-A*-B$	$-B-(-A98+7+65+432*-1)$
1250	02076	$1234-5-67+89+A-B$	$-B+A98-(7+65)+432+1$
1251	02077	$1234+5+6*7+89-AB$	$BA+987-65+432-1$
1252	02078	$1234-5-6+7-89+AB$	$BA+987-(65+432*-1)$
1253	02079	$123+456+7-(-89A+B)$	$BA9-8+76*5-43-21$
1254	02080	$123+4*(5-67)-89*(-A-B)$	$BA9+87-(-6+5*-43)-(-2-1)$
1255	02081	$1234-56+78*(-9+A)-B$	$BA9-(87-654+321)$
1256	02082	$1+2-(-3+4-567-(89A+B))$	$B+A9+87+6+5+4*321$
1257	02083	$1234-56+78-9*(-A+B)$	$BA+9+87+6-5-4*321$
1258	02084	$1-23*-45-(67+8)*9-AB$	$-B+A9*(8+7)-(-65+4-3)*-21$
1259	02085	$1234+5-6-78-9+AB$	$B+A98-76-5-(-432+1)$
125A	02086	$12*(3-(4-56)+78-9-A+B)$	$B+A98-76-5-432*-1$
125B	02087	$123+456-(7-89A-B)$	$B+A98-76-5+432+1$
1260	02088	$1234-(-5+67)-(-89+A)+B$	$-BA-9+8-7*6*-54-321$
1261	02089	$1-2-(34+5)+678+9*AB$	$-B+A98+7-65+432*1$
1262	02090	$-1+2345-(-6*-78+9A*B)$	$B+A98-7-(-65+4-321)$
1263	02091	$1234-(56-(7-(-89+A))))-B$	$-B-(-A98-76)-(-5-4)+321$
1264	02092	$1234-56-7-8+9A-B$	$B-A+987-(-65-432-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1265	02093	$-1-2-3-4^*-5-(-67+8-9A)^*B$	$-B+A98+76+5-(4-321)$
1266	02094	$1-23+4^*5^*(-6+7)^*(89-A+B)$	$BA-(9-87)+6^*5-4^*-321$
1267	02095	$-1-2+34+567+89A-B$	$B+A98-(76-(5+432))-1$
1268	02096	$12-(3+4)+567-(8+9A^*-B)$	$B+A98-76+5-432^*-1$
1269	02097	$1-(2-34)-(-567-89A+B)$	$B+A98-(76-5)+432+1$
126A	02098	$1234-5-67+89-(-A-B)$	$BA9-8+(7-6)^*-54+321$
126B	02099	$1234+56-7+89-AB$	$BA9-8+7-6-54+321$
1270	02100	$1234-56+7-8+9^*A+B$	$-B-A+(-98+76)^*-54+321$
1271	02101	$123-(-456-7)-(-89A-B)$	$BA9+8-7-(6+54-321)$
1272	02102	$1234+5-(-67+8)-9-A-B$	$B-(A98+7)+6^*(-5+432^*1)$
1273	02103	$1+2-34^*(5-6)^*-7^*-8-9-AB$	$B-A98-7-6^*(5-432)+1$
1274	02104	$1234-56+78-9+A+B$	$B+A98+7+65-(4-321)$
1275	02105	$1234-(5-(6-78)-9-AB)$	$B+A98+76-5-4+321$
1276	02106	$12-3-(-45^*6^*7+(8-9)^*-AB)$	$-B+A9+876-(-543+21)$
1277	02107	$1234-56-7-8-9+AB$	$B-(-A98+7^*-65+4-(3+2^*1))$
1278	02108	$1234-(56+7-8)-(-9A+B)$	$-B+A98+7^*65-(4-3)+21$
1279	02109	$1234-5-6+7^*8+9+A-B$	$-BA9-87-65^*-43+2^*-1$
127A	02110	$1-23-(4-5)-(-678-9^*AB)$	$B+A-(-987-(65+432-1))$
127B	02111	$1+23^*-4+567-(8-9AB)$	$-BA9+8^*(7-(-654+321))$
1280	02112	$1-(-23-4-(567+89A+B))$	$BA9+8-(-7+65)+4+321$
1281	02113	$1234+56+7+89-AB$	$BA9+8-7-(-6+54)+321$
1282	02114	$1234-(-5-67)+89-AB$	$BA98-76^*-5^*(-4-32+1)$
1283	02115	$-1+23-4^*-5^*(-6+78+9A)-B$	$B+A98+76+5-4+321$
1284	02116	$-1-2+3^*456+78-9+A^*B$	$BA9+8+7^*-6-5^*4+321$
1285	02117	$1234-(-5+6-78-(-9-A-B))$	$B+A^*9-(-876-543-2-1)$
1286	02118	$1^*-2+34-(-567-89A)+B$	$-B+A98-(-7-6)-5^*4^*(-3-21)$
1287	02119	$1-2-(-34-567-(89A+B))$	$B+A98-76^*-5+43^*-2^*-1$
1288	02120	$1234+5+67-8+9-A-B$	$B+A9^*8+765-4-(3+2)+1$
1289	02121	$-1+2+34-(-567-89A-B)$	$BA-9-(-876-543+21)$
128A	02122	$12+3^*456-7^*(89-AB)$	$-B-A98-(7+65^*(-43-(-2-1)))$
128B	02123	$1234+56-(-78-9+A^*B)$	$B+A98+76-(-5-4)+321$
1290	02124	$-1^*-2^*(3-4)^*(-5-(678+9^*A)-B)$	$-B+A9+8^*7+(-65-4+3)^*-21$
1291	02125	$1234+5+6+7-(-8^*9+A)-B$	$BA9+87-(6^*-54-3^*-21)$
1292	02126	$123+456-(-7-8-9A^*B)$	$BA9+87+65^*4+3-(2-1)$
1293	02127	$1+23^*-4+567+8+9AB$	$BA9+8-(-7-6+54-321)$
1294	02128	$-12^*(-3-45+6-78-9+A-B)$	$B+A9+876+543-21$
1295	02129	$12+3+45+67^*8+9AB$	$-B+A9-(-876-543)-2^*1$
1296	02130	$1234+5-67-(-8-9-AB)$	$BA9-8-76^*-5+4^*3^*-2-1$
1297	02131	$-1234-5^*-6^*78+9AB$	$-B-A+9-87^*-6+(54-3)^*21$
1298	02132	$-1^*2^*(3+4-(-5+678))+9-AB$	$-B+A98+7^*65-(-43+2+1)$
1299	02133	$-1-23+456+78+9AB$	$-B-(-A+9)-(-87^*6+(-54+3)^*21)$
129A	02134	$-1^*(23-456-78-9AB)$	$BA9-8-(-7+6^*-54)-32^*-1$
129B	02135	$-1-2+3^*45-(-6^*78-9AB)$	$-B+A9^*87-6543-2^*1$
12A0	02136	$1234-(5-6^*-7-8)-(-9+A^*-B)$	$BA9-8-76+54+321$
12A1	02137	$1234-5+6+78+9-A-B$	$BA9-87+6+54+321$
12A2	02138	$-1+23-(-45^*-6^*-7-(8+9))-AB$	$-B-(-A-987+6)+543-21$
12A3	02139	$-1-(-2-3)-(-4^*567+89^*A)-B$	$BA-(-9-876)-(-543+21)$
12A4	02140	$1234+5+67+8-9-A+B$	$B-A+987-6+543-21$
12A5	02141	$1234-(5-6-78)-(-9+A-B)$	$B+A^*(9+8)-7^*(-65^*4+3+21)$
12A6	02142	$-12^*(3-4+5+67-89-AB)$	$-B+A98-7-(6+5-432-1)$
12A7	02143	$1+23+4^*-5+678+9^*AB$	$B-A-(-9+8^*7^*6^*-5+4-321)$
12A8	02144	$-12+345-(6-7)-8^*(9+A)^*-B$	$BA-9+876-(-543+2^*1)$
12A9	02145	$1^*23-456-78^*(-9-A-B)$	$BA+987-6-5+432+1$
12AA	02146	$1234-5-(6-78+9^*(A-B))$	$-BA+987-(-654+32+1)$
12AB	02147	$1234-(-5-6)-(7-8+9^*-A)-B$	$-BA+987+654+32^*-1$
12B0	02148	$123+456-78+9AB$	$BA9-87-65+432+1$
12B1	02149	$1234+5+6+78-9+A-B$	$-BA+98-76-5^*(4-321)$
12B2	02150	$1234-5+67-(-8+9-A-B)$	$-B+A98-7-(6-(5+432-1))$
12B3	02151	$1234+56-(7-(-89+AB))$	$B+A+987-6-5^*-4^*32-1$
12B4	02152	$1234-5-6-7-8-9+AB$	$B+A9+876+543-2+1$
12B5	02153	$123-4+567+8-9^*-AB$	$BA+987-6+5-(-432+1)$
12B6	02154	$-1-2-3^*(45+67^*-8-9-AB)$	$-B-A9^*-8+765+43-2-1$
12B7	02155	$1-2+(-3-4+5)^*(-678-(-9+AB))$	$BA-(-987-(6-5+432-1))$
12B8	02156	$-1^*(2+3-456-78-9AB)$	$-B-A-(-987-6-543-2+1)$
12B9	02157	$-1+234+5^*67+8+9AB$	$-BA+987-(-654+3+21)$
12BA	02158	$12-3+456-(7-8^*9^*(A+B))$	$BA9-(8+7)-(-6-5-4-321)$
12BB	02159	$1+234+5^*67-(-8-9AB)$	$BA9-(-876+543+21)$
1300	02160	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4+56-7)^*(8+9-(A-B))$	$BA9-8-7+6-5+4+321$
1301	02161	$1+2-3+456+78+9AB$	$BA9-(-87-65^*4-32)-1$
1302	02162	$1+23+4-5-(-678+9^*-AB)$	$-B-(-A-987)-(-6-(543-2+1))$
1303	02163	$1-2+3+456+78+9AB$	$-BA+987+654-(-3+21)$
1304	02164	$1+23-4-(-5-678-9^*AB)$	$B+A98-(7+6-(-5+432+1))$
1305	02165	$-1-(-2-3-456)-(-78-9AB)$	$BA-(-9-876)-(-543-(2-1))$
1306	02166	$1234+5+67-89+AB$	$-B+A98+7-6+5+432+1$
1307	02167	$1234-5-6-(-78-(9+A+B))$	$BA+987-(-6-5)+432+1$
1308	02168	$1^*-2^*(3-4+5-6-78+9^*-A^*B)$	$BA9+8-(7-6+5-(-4+321))$
1309	02169	$1234+56-78+9A+B$	$BA9-8-7+654-321$
130A	02170	$1234+5+6+78+(-9+A)^*B$	$BA9+8+7-6-5-4+321$
130B	02171	$1234+5+6+78-9+A+B$	$BA-9-(-876-543)+21$
1310	02172	$12-3+456-(-78-9AB)$	$B+A^*(98+76)+54+32-1$
1311	02173	$1234-5+6+7+8+9^*A+B$	$B-(-A98+7)-6-(-5+432^*-1)$
1312	02174	$1234+5+6-7-8-9+AB$	$BA9-8+7+6-5-(-4-321)$
1313	02175	$-1+2^*(34-56+789-A+B)$	$BA9-8-(-765+432+1)$
1314	02176	$1^*-2-34+567-8+9AB$	$-B+A-(-987-(6+543))-(-2+1)$
1315	02177	$1234-(-56-7-8)-(-9-A-B)$	$-B+A98+765+4-321$
1316	02178	$12-(-3-456)-(-78-9AB)$	$B+A9-(-876-543-21)$
1317	02179	$1234-5+6+7+8+9A-B$	$B+A-(-9+87-6-5)^*(-43+21)$
1318	02180	$-12-34+567+8+9AB$	$B-(A-987-6)-(-543-2-1)$
1319	02181	$1+2-34+567-8+9AB$	$BA9-8+76^*5+43-21$
131A	02182	$1+2-34^*-5+6^*78+9AB$	$B+A+987-(-6-543)-2-1$
131B	02183	$1234+5-6+7-8+9A+B$	$BA9-(8-7)-(-654+321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1320	02184	$-12*(3-4)*(-567-8*-9A+B)$	$-BA+98+(-76+5)*(-4+3-21)$
1321	02185	$1234-5+6-(7+8)-(-9A-B)$	$-BA+987-(-654-3+2)-1$
1322	02186	$-1-(23+4-567+8)+9AB$	$B+A98-7+6-(-5-432)+1$
1323	02187	$-1+2345-(-6-78*(-9-A)+B)$	$BA9+876-543+2+1$
1324	02188	$-123+45+67+(-8-9)*-AB$	$BA9-8+76-(54-321)$
1325	02189	$1+23+456+78+9AB$	$BA-(-9-876)-(-543-21)$
1326	02190	$1*234-5*(-67-8)+9AB$	$B-A+987-6+543+21$
1327	02191	$1234-5*(67-89+A-B)$	$B+A98+765-4-321$
1328	02192	$12-(34-567)-8+9AB$	$BA9-87-6*(5+43*2*-1)$
1329	02193	$1-(2+34-567-8-9AB)$	$BA9+8+765-432+1$
132A	02194	$-1-23+4+567-(8-9AB)$	$B+A+987+6+543-2-1$
132B	02195	$-1+2-34-(-567-8-9AB)$	$BA9-(-876+5*-4*-32*1)$
1330	02196	$1-2*(-34+56-789)+A+B$	$-B+A98-(7*-6+5-432*1)$
1331	02197	$1+2-34+567+8+9AB$	$BA9+87-6*-54+3*(-2+1)$
1332	02198	$1234-(5-6+7)-(-8-9-AB)$	$B+A98+7-(-6-(5+432-1))$
1333	02199	$-1+2*-3-45*6*-7-8-(-9-(-A-B))$	$B+A98+765+4-321$
1334	02200	$-1*-2*(3-4-(-5-678-9)+AB)$	$-BA-9-(-8*-76+5*-432)+1$
1335	02201	$1+2-3-45+678+9A*B$	$BA-98-76+5*(-4+321)$
1336	02202	$-12-3-(4-5-6)-(-7+89*(-A-B))$	$B-A+987+6+543+21$
1337	02203	$-12+3-4+567-8+9AB$	$BA9-(-87+6)-(-54-321)$
1338	02204	$1-23-(4-567-8-9AB)$	$BA9+8-(-76+54)+321$
1339	02205	$1234+56+7*-8-(-9A-B)$	$-B+A98+7*6+5+432-1$
133A	02206	$1*-2*(-3*45-678-9+A+B)$	$B+A+9-8-(-7-65)*(43-21)$
133B	02207	$-1+2*345-6+789+AB$	$-BA+987+654-3+21$
1340	02208	$-1-2-3-4+567-(8-9AB)$	$-BA-9-8-7*-65+4*321$
1341	02209	$-1+2345-6*78-9*AB$	$BA9+876-543+21$
1342	02210	$-1-(23-4-567-(8+9AB))$	$B+A-(-987+6)-(-543-21)$
1343	02211	$1234+5+6+7-(-8-9A-B)$	$BA9+8-(-7-6)-(-5*4-321)$
1344	02212	$-1-(23+4+56-(78+9A)*B)$	$BA9-(87+6)-(-5-432+1)$
1345	02213	$-12-3-(4-567-8-9AB)$	$BA9-(8+7-(-6+54)-321)$
1346	02214	$1+2-3-4+567-8+9AB$	$B-(A98-7*(-65+432)*1)$
1347	02215	$1234-5*-67-89-AB$	$BA9+87-(-6+54-321)$
1348	02216	$-12+3*4-(-567+8-9AB)$	$B-(A9+8)-76+54*-32*-1$
1349	02217	$-1-23-4-(5-(678+9A*B))$	$-BA-9*8-(7-6)-54*32*-1$
134A	02218	$1234+5-(67-89-AB)$	$BA+9-(-8-(-76+543))*2+1$
134B	02219	$1-23-4-(5-678)-9A*-B$	$BA+9+(87-(-654-3))*2*1$
1350	02220	$1-(-2-3)-(4-567+8-9AB)$	$-BA9+8-(-76-(54+3))*21$
1351	02221	$-123+4+5-(-678-9AB)$	$B-A98-7*(-65-4-321)$
1352	02222	$1-2-3*-4-(-5+6-7+89*(-A-B))$	$-BA+987+654-(-32+1)$
1353	02223	$1234+56+7+89-A-B$	$-B+A98-(76-543+2)-1$
1354	02224	$-1-2-3-(4-567)-(-8-9AB)$	$-BA+987+654-(-32-1)$
1355	02225	$123-4+567+89A-B$	$BA9-8-7+6+54+321$
1356	02226	$1*(-2-34)*(5+67-(8+9A+B))$	$-B-(-A+98)-76-54*-32+1$
1357	02227	$1234+5+6+7+8+9A-B$	$BA9-(8-7)-6-(-54-321)$
1358	02228	$1234-5-(-6-78+9*-A+B)$	$BA-9*-8*(76-54+3)+2*-1$
1359	02229	$1234-56-7+89+AB$	$BA9-(-8+7+6-54)+321$
135A	02230	$1+2-3-4+567+8+9AB$	$BA9+8*(-7+6)*-54+3*2-1$
135B	02231	$1234+56-7+89-A+B$	$BA-(-987-(65+432-1))$
1360	02232	$1234-56-(-78-9)+AB$	$B-A9+8*-76-5*-432*1$
1361	02233	$1234+5-(6+7*-8)-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A*-98+(-765-(4-3)+2)*-1$
1362	02234	$-12+3-45*6*-7+8-(9-A)*B$	$BA9-87+6+5+432-1$
1363	02235	$-1-23+4*567-8*9A+B$	$BA9-87+6+(-5-432)*-1$
1364	02236	$-1+2-(3-(4+567))+8+9AB$	$BA9-8-7-(-65-4-321)$
1365	02237	$1234-5-6*(7-8-9-(A+B))$	$-BA+9-8*7-6-54*-32*1$
1366	02238	$1234+56+7-8+9A-B$	$-BA9-8+7+65*43+21$
1367	02239	$1234+5+67-(8-9A+B)$	$BA9+8-76-5-(-432+1)$
1368	02240	$1-2-(-3-4-567-8)+9AB$	$BA9+8*7+654-321$
1369	02241	$12-3-4+567+8+9AB$	$BA9+8-(7-6)-(-54-321)$
136A	02242	$1-(-23+4)-(-567+8-9AB)$	$-B+A98+7+65+432-1$
136B	02243	$1234-56-(-7-89)+AB$	$BA9-(8-76)-(-5+4)+321$
1370	02244	$-12+34+567-8+9AB$	$-B+A98+7+65+432+1$
1371	02245	$123+4*5-67*(89-AB)$	$-B+A98+76-5+432+1$
1372	02246	$1234-(-5-67-(89-A))+B$	$BA9-8-7*-65-4-3*-2*1$
1373	02247	$-1+2-3*-4+567-(-8-9AB)$	$B+A98-76-(-543+2-1)$
1374	02248	$-1-(-23-4)+567-(8-9AB)$	$BA9-8+7-65-(-432+1)$
1375	02249	$1234-(-5-(67-(-8+9)-A*-B))$	$BA9-8-(-7+65-432*1)$
1376	02250	$1234+56+7*(8+9)-(-A+B)$	$B-A98+765+43*21$
1377	02251	$1234-5+67-8+9A+B$	$-B+A98-76+543+21$
1378	02252	$-12+3+4*567+8*-9A+B$	$B-A-98-(-7*65+4*-321)$
1379	02253	$123-(45-678+9*-AB)$	$B-A+987+654+3*-21$
137A	02254	$1234-(-5+6-(78+9A-B))$	$-B+A98+76+5-432*-1$
137B	02255	$1234+56-7+8-9+AB$	$-B+A98-(-76-5-432-1)$
1380	02256	$-1+23-4-(-567-8-9AB)$	$BA-98*(-7-6-5)-(-43+21)$
1381	02257	$1+2+34*5+67*(-89+AB)$	$B-A-9-8-7-6*-5*(43+21)$
1382	02258	$-1-2-(34-(-5+67))-(-8-9)*-AB$	$BA9+87-(6-(-5-4)-321)$
1383	02259	$-1+2+34+567-8+9AB$	$-B+A98+7*65-(4+3)*-21$
1384	02260	$-12-(-34-567-8-9AB)$	$-BA+987+654+3*21$
1385	02261	$1-(-2-34-567)-(-8-9AB)$	$BA9-(8-76-5)-(-4-321)$
1386	02262	$1+2+34+5-6-7+(-8-9)*-AB$	$-B-A9+87-6-5*(-4-321)$
1387	02263	$-1-(-2+3)-(-45+67)*(-8-9)-(-A-B)$	$BA9-8*7+6*(54+32-1)$
1388	02264	$-1-(-23-4)-(-567-8)+9AB$	$B-(-A98-7)-(-65-432+1)$
1389	02265	$1234+56-(-7-89-(A+B))$	$-BA-(-9+8)-(-76-54*(32+1))$
138A	02266	$-1+2-(-34-5)*67-(-8-9A*-B)$	$B-A+98*-7-(-65-4)*-32-1$
138B	02267	$1234-5+67+8-(-9A-B)$	$-B+A*98-(-765+4-32+1)$
1390	02268	$-12*(-3+4+56+7-89-AB)$	$BA9+87-6-(-5+4-321)$
1391	02269	$1234-(-5+6-78)-(9-AB)$	$-BA+9+8-7*6*(-5-43-(2-1))$
1392	02270	$-1*2*(-3+4)*-5*(6+78+9A+B)$	$BA9+87+6-(-5+4-321)$
1393	02271	$1234-5+6+78-9+AB$	$B+A*98-(76+5-43)*-21$
1394	02272	$1234+5+67-(8-9-AB)$	$BA*(-9-(-8+7+6))-(-5-4*-3*-2-1))$
1395	02273	$1234+56-7+8+9+AB$	$B+A98-76-(-543-21)$
1396	02274	$1234-5-6-(7-89-AB)$	$-BA-(9+8-7+6)+54*-32*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1397	02275	-12+34-5+678+9A*B	BA9+87*65-4321
1398	02276	1234+56+7+8+9A+B	BA9+87-(6-5)-(-4-321)
1399	02277	1-(-2-34)+567-(-8-9AB)	B+A98+76+5-(-432-1)
139A	02278	-1+2-3*(-4-567)-(-8+9)-AB	BA9+87+6-5+4+321
139B	02279	-1*(2-34-5)*(67-(-89+AB))	-BA+9-(8+7+6-54*32-1)
13A0	02280	1+23+4*(567-89-AB)	BA9+87-(-6-5)-4+321
13A1	02281	1234+5+6+78-9+AB	BA9-8-(7*6-5-432)-1
13A2	02282	1*-2*(3+4)*(56+7-89-AB)	B-A*-98+765+4-3+21
13A3	02283	-1+23+45+6-7+89*(A+B)	BA9-8-7-6*5+432+1
13A4	02284	1234+5-6-7+89+AB	B-(-A+9)-8-(76+5)*4*3*2*-1
13A5	02285	-12+34+5-(-678+9A*-B)	BA9+8*7-6*(-54+3-21)
13A6	02286	-1-(-2+3+4)-(-5*(6+7))-(-8-9)*-AB)	BA9+8-7*-65+43-21
13A7	02287	-12-3-(-4-56)+7-(-8-9)*AB	BA9+87+654-321
13A8	02288	1234+5+67-(-8-9-AB)	-B+A+987+654-32*1
13A9	02289	1234-5+6+78+9+AB	BA9-8+7-6*5*-4+321
13AA	02290	12+3+4+5+6*7*8-9AB	-B-(-A98+7-6)-(-543+21)
13AB	02291	-123+45*6*7+89+AB	B-(A-987-654+32-1)
13B0	02292	-1*2*(3-(-45-67))-(-89A+B))	BA-9+8-(-7*65*4-(-3-2)*1)
13B1	02293	1-2+3*(4+567)-8-(9A-B)	BA+987-(-6-543+21)
13B2	02294	1-234*-5*-6+(789-A)*B	BA9-876-5+4*321
13B3	02295	1-234+5*67+(-8-9)*-AB	BA-9-8+765*(-4+3+2+1)
13B4	02296	123+456-7*-8+9AB	BA9-87*-6+5*-4*3+21
13B5	02297	-1+234+567-8-9*-AB	-B+A-(-987-65*4*-3)-21
13B6	02298	1234-(-5+6-(7+89+AB))	-B-(-A-987)-(-654+3+21)
13B7	02299	12+3-4+5+6-7+(-8-9)*-AB	B*(-A+98-(7-65+4-32)-1)
13B8	02300	1234-5+6+7+89+AB	B+A98-7-6+543-21
13B9	02301	-12-34+5*(-678+9AB)	-BA-9+8+7+6+54*32-1
13BA	02302	-1-(23+45)-(-678-9AB)	BA9-(87-(65+432)-1)
13BB	02303	12-3*45*-6-(78-9AB)	BA+987-6-(-543+2+1)
1400	02304	-1*-2*-3*(4+567-8+9*-AB)	-B+A98+7+6-(-543+21)
1401	02305	123+4-5+678-9*-AB	BA9+8+7+6*-5*-4+321
1402	02306	1*-2*(-34+5-67+89*-A+B)	B-A-(-987-654)+3-21
1403	02307	123-4+5-(-678-9*AB)	BA+987-6+543+2-1
1404	02308	1-(-2345+6*-7*-8)-9A*B	B-A*-98+765+43+2-1
1405	02309	1+2*-34+5+678+9AB	-BA-987+65*(43-2+1)
1406	02310	1234+5*67+8*(-9-A)+B	B*-A*(-9-(8+7))-(-6-5-4-(3-2)+1))
1407	02311	1-2*-345-(67+8-9AB)	B+A+987-(-654+32-1)
1408	02312	-1+2+3*4*56+78+9AB	BA9-8-(7-6)-5+432-1
1409	02313	-1+234+567+8-9*-AB	BA9-8-7+6-5+432*1
140A	02314	1234-5*-67-(-8+9A+B)	B-A-9-87-6+54*32-1
140B	02315	1+2*(-34-5-(67-89A-B))	-BA+9*(87-6-5-4+3)*(2+1)
1410	02316	-1+2-34+5*(-678+9AB)	BA9-8+76+54+321
1411	02317	1234+56-(7*-8-(9A+B))	BA+987-(-6-543)-(-2-1)
1412	02318	1-(-2+34-5*(-678+9AB))	-B-(-A98-7+6-543-(2-1))
1413	02319	-12+3-(45-678-9AB)	BA+987+6+543+2-1
1414	02320	-1-2-3*-4*-5+678+9AB	-B+A98+7-6+543+2+1
1415	02321	-12+34*5+678-9*-AB	BA+987-(-6-543-2-1)
1416	02322	1234+5+67+8*9+A*B	B+A98-7-6+543-2-1
1417	02323	-1-2*3-45-(-678-9AB)	B-A+987+654-3+2*-1
1418	02324	-12-34-5+678+9AB	B-A-9-8-76*(54-32)*-1
1419	02325	1234+56+78-9-A*-B	-B-(-A-987)-(-654+3+2*-1)
141A	02326	-12-34+5*(-6-7*-8*9)+A*-B	-B+A98+7+6+543-2-1
141B	02327	1-23*-4+567-8+9AB	B-A+987+654-3+2*1
1420	02328	-1-(-2+3)-45+678+9AB	BA9-8+7+6-5+432+1
1421	02329	1*2-(3+45-678-9AB)	-B+A-98+7+6+54*32+1
1422	02330	-1-2+3-45+678+9AB	-B+A98-(-765+4*-3*-21)
1423	02331	1*-2+3-45+678+9AB	BA9+87-(6-54)+321
1424	02332	123+456+78+9AB	BA9-8*-76-54-32+1
1425	02333	-1-(-23-45)+678-9A*-B	B-A+987+654-(-3-2*1)
1426	02334	-12-34-(-5-678-9AB)	B-A-(-987-654-(3+2))+1
1427	02335	-1-(2+34)-5-(-678-9AB)	BA9+876-5-432-1
1428	02336	1-(-2-(3-45))-(-678-9AB)	BA9-8+7+6-(-5-432)-1
1429	02337	1-2-34-5+678+9AB	BA9-8-(-765-4+321)
142A	02338	-123-4*-56*(-7+8+9)-AB	-B+A+98-76+543*(2+1)
142B	02339	-1+2-34-5+678+9AB	-BA-9876+543*21
1430	02340	1234+56-7+89+A*B	BA9+8-7-(-6-(5+432)-1)
1431	02341	12-3+45*-6*-7+89+A-B	-B+A*(9-8)-76+54*-32*-1
1432	02342	1234-5*-67-8+9*A*B	BA9+8+7+6-(5-432+1)
1433	02343	1234+56+78+9-A*-B	BA+987+6+543+21
1434	02344	123-45-(-6+7+89)*(A-B)	B-(-A9+87)-6-543*(-2-1)
1435	02345	-1-2-34+5-(-678-9AB)	BA9+8+765-4-321
1436	02346	1234-(-56-78+9)+AB	-B+A+98+7*65*4-3*-21
1437	02347	12-(-3+45)-(-678-9AB)	BA9+876-(-5+432-1)
1438	02348	1-(23-(-4-5+678+9AB))	B-(-A98-(7-(-6-543+2+1)))
1439	02349	-1*23*(4-5+6-(-7-(8-9A+B)))	B-(-A98-(7+6+543)+2*1)
143A	02350	-1*2*(-3+4)*(5+67-89A+B)	BA9-87-6+543-21
143B	02351	1+2-34+5+678+9AB	-B-A98-(7-65*43+2*1)
1440	02352	-12+3+4*-5-(-678-9AB)	B-(-A98-765-4*-3*21)
1441	02353	1234+56+78+9A+B	BA9+8+765+4-321
1442	02354	-1-23+4-5-(-678-9AB)	BA9+87+65+4+321
1443	02355	-1*(2+3)*(-456+789)*(A-B)	BA9-8+76-5*4*(-3-21)
1444	02356	1-(23-4)-(-5-678-9AB)	BA9-87+6-5*-4*(32-1)
1445	02357	1-23+(4-5)*-678+9AB	BA-9*8+7+6*5*(-43-21)
1446	02358	1+23-45+678+9AB	BA9+87*6+54-32+1
1447	02359	-1+2*34+5*-6+(78+9A)*B	BA9+8-7-6*-5-(-432-1)
1448	02360	1*(2+3)*(-4+5-678+9AB)	B-A+987-6*-5*(4+3+21)
1449	02361	1234-(-56+7)-(-89-AB)	-BA-(9-(876-5))+43*21
144A	02362	12-(34-5)+678+9AB	BA9-(87-6)-(-543+21)
144B	02363	-12-(-3+4+5)-(-678-9AB)	-B+A+987+654-(-32+1)
1450	02364	-1-23+4+5-(-678-9AB)	-B+A+987+654-32*-1
1451	02365	-12-3-(-4+5-678-9AB)	-B+A+987+654+32+1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1452	02366	$1+2*(-3-4+56+789)-(-A-B)$	$B-A+987-(-654-32*1)$
1453	02367	$1234+5-6*-7*8-9-A-B$	$B-A-(-987-654-32-1)$
1454	02368	$-1-2-3-4-5+678+9AB$	$-B-A98+7+65*43-(-2+1)$
1455	02369	$1*-2-3456+7*(-8+9*AB)$	$BA-(98+76-54*32-1)$
1456	02370	$1234-5*-6*7+89-(-A+B)$	$BA+9*-8*-7*6-(543+21)$
1457	02371	$-12+3+4-5+678+9AB$	$-BA-9+876-(-5+43*-21)$
1458	02372	$123-(45-678-9A*B)$	$B-A+9+87-6+5*(-4+321)$
1459	02373	$-1-2+3*-4-(-5-(678+9AB))$	$BA9-(87+6-543)-2*1$
145A	02374	$1*2*(-3+4-56-7+89A-B)$	$BA9-87-6-(-543+2-1)$
145B	02375	$1234+56+7+89+AB$	$BA9-87-6-543*(-2+1)$
1460	02376	$-1*(-234-5+6+78+9A)*B$	$BA9-87-6+543+2-1$
1461	02377	$-1-(-23+4-5*(-678+9AB))$	$BA+987-(-6-5)*(43+21)$
1462	02378	$-1+2+3-4-5+678+9AB$	$-BA+9*-8*(-76+5+43-2+1)$
1463	02379	$1+2*-3-(4-5-(678+9AB))$	$-BA+9+876-5+43*21$
1464	02380	$-12*(-345+67+89+AB)$	$B+A-9+8+765+43*21$
1465	02381	$-1-(-234+5)-(-67*-8-9AB)$	$-B+A98-(-76-543+21)$
1466	02382	$-1+2-(3+4-5)+678+9AB$	$-BA+9-8+76-54*32+1$
1467	02383	$-12+34*56-7-89-AB$	$BA9-8-(76-543+2+1)$
1468	02384	$-1-2*-34*5*6+78-9A+B$	$BA9-87+6+543-2-1$
1469	02385	$1234+5-(6*7*-8-9)-(A+B)$	$B+A+987-(-654-32)-1$
146A	02386	$1+2*(-345+6)*(7-8)+9AB$	$-BA98-76*-5*-43*(-2+1)$
146B	02387	$1*-2-3+4-(-5-(678+9AB))$	$B+A-9+8+7*65+4*321$
1470	02388	$1-2-3+4+5+678+9AB$	$-B+A+98-7-6*5*(-43-21)$
1471	02389	$-1+23-4*5-(-678-9AB)$	$BA9-87+6-(543+2)*-1$
1472	02390	$-12+3-4*(5+67*8)-9A+B$	$BA9-(87-6)-(-543-2)+1$
1473	02391	$-1234-5-6*-7*(89-A+B)$	$-B+A98-7+654-3*21$
1474	02392	$-12-(-3-4*5-678)+9AB$	$-B-A98+7-65*-43+21$
1475	02393	$123-(-4-567)-8+9AB$	$-BA-98-7*6*-54-32+1$
1476	02394	$-12-34*56-78-9-AB$	$BA+987+654+3*-21$
1477	02395	$1-(2+3)+45-6-(-7-89)*(A+B)$	$-BA+9-(-87+6-54*32+1)$
1478	02396	$-1-(-2-3-4-5)-(-678-9AB)$	$-BA+9*(-87-6*-5*4*3+21)$
1479	02397	$-12+3*(4+567)-8+9-A+B$	$-BA+9-(-87+6-54*32)+1$
147A	02398	$1-(-2-3-4-5-(678+9AB))$	$B-A9-87+65*(-4+32)+1$
147B	02399	$12+3+4-5+678+9AB$	$BA9+8-76+543-(2+1)$
1480	02400	$-1+23-4-5+678+9AB$	$BA9-87-6+543+21$
1481	02401	$12+3-4+5-(-678-9AB)$	$-B-A9+87+6+54*-32*-1$
1482	02402	$1-(-23+4+5)-(-678-9AB)$	$B-A9*-8-(-7-65)-43*-21$
1483	02403	$1*-23*(45*-6-(7-89-AB))$	$-B+A98+76+543-2-1$
1484	02404	$-12-(-34+5)-(-678-9AB)$	$BA9-(-8-(-7+65))-(-432-1)$
1485	02405	$-1-2*-345-6+7+8+9AB$	$-B+A98+76+543-(2-1)$
1486	02406	$-1-2-3*(-4-567)+8-9-A+B$	$BA9-(-8+7)-(-65-432-1)$
1487	02407	$-1+234+567-(-89A-B)$	$-B+A98+76+543+2-1$
1488	02408	$-1-23+45+678+9AB$	$-B+A98+76+543-2*-1$
1489	02409	$1+2-3*(45-(678+9+A*-B))$	$BA9-8*-76+5*(-4-3+2)+1$
148A	02410	$1-23-(-45-678-9AB)$	$B-A9+87-6-54*-32-1$
148B	02411	$1234-5*(6+7-(89-A)+B)$	$BA9-8-76+543+21$
1490	02412	$1+23-4-(-5-678-9AB)$	$BA9-87+6+543+21$
1491	02413	$1234-(-56-78+9*(-A-B))$	$-B-A9-(-8-7*6*-5*-4*3-21)$
1492	02414	$-12+34+5+678+9AB$	$-BA*(-9-(87-65-(-4-(3-21))))$
1493	02415	$-1-2+34-(5-678-9AB)$	$BA+9-8+(765+43)*-2*-1$
1494	02416	$-1+2+345-67*-8+9A*B$	$-B-A9+8-(76-(-5+4))*(-3-21)$
1495	02417	$1-(2-34-(-5-(-678-9AB)))$	$-BA+9-(-8-76+54)*3*21$
1496	02418	$1+234+567-8+9A*B$	$BA9-(-87+6)-(5-(432-1))$
1497	02419	$-12-3+45+678+9AB$	$-BA+98+7+6+54*32*1$
1498	02420	$12+3-4*-5-(-678-9AB)$	$B+A9+8+(-765-43)*2*-1$
1499	02421	$1+2-(-34+5)-(-678-9AB)$	$BA9+8+76-5+432+1$
149A	02422	$1+2+34*56-78-9A-B$	$BA+987+6+5*(-4-3)*-21$
149B	02423	$1234+56*7-89*(-A+B)$	$B+A9-8+(7-6*54*3)*-2+1$
14A0	02424	$1*2*(3-4*(-56+78))*(9-A-B)$	$-B-A-(9-8-7-(6+54*32+1))$
14A1	02425	$-12+3-(-45-678)+9AB$	$B+A9*(8+7)+(-6+5-4)*-321$
14A2	02426	$-1+2345-67-8-9AB$	$B+A-(98-76)-54*-32-1$
14A3	02427	$-1+2345-(-6-(-78-9AB))$	$-B+A98-7+654-(32+1)$
14A4	02428	$1+2345-67-8-9AB$	$BA9+87-6+5+432-1$
14A5	02429	$-1-(-2-34)-(-5-678-9AB)$	$B+A98+76-(-543-2)-1$
14A6	02430	$-1-(2+3-45)-(-678-9AB)$	$-B-A98-7-65*(-43-2+1)$
14A7	02431	$1-(-23+4*-5-678-9AB)$	$-B-(-A98-76-543-21)$
14A8	02432	$12+34-5+678+9AB$	$BA+987+654-(32-1)$
14A9	02433	$-123+4*(567-8-(9+AB))$	$B-A-(98-7+65*(4-32+1))$
14AA	02434	$123+4+5+678-9A*-B$	$BA9+876-54-321$
14AB	02435	$-1*(2+345)*(67-89+A+B)$	$-BA-98+7*-6*-54-(-3*2+1)$
14B0	02436	$-1-(2-3-(45+678)-9AB)$	$-B-(A-(98-76))-(-54*-32+1)$
14B1	02437	$-1*(2-3-45-(678+9AB))$	$B+A-9*-8*7*6+5-432+1$
14B2	02438	$1-2+3+45-(-678-9AB)$	$BA9-8-(7+6-543+21)$
14B3	02439	$-1-234-5*6*-78+9A-B$	$-BA9-8*(-76-(5-432))*-1$
14B4	02440	$1*2+34-56*7*-8+9A*-B$	$BA9+87+6-(-5-432+1)$
14B5	02441	$12-3-(4*-5*6+(78+9A)*-B)$	$-B+A98-7*(65+43)*(-2+1)$
14B6	02442	$-1+2345-67+8-9AB$	$-B+A98-(-7-654+32*1)$
14B7	02443	$-1*(-2345+67-8+9AB)$	$-B+A98+7+654-32+1$
14B8	02444	$1+2345-67+8-9AB$	$-B+A98-7-(-654-3)-21$
14B9	02445	$123-4*-5+678-9A*-B$	$B-A-(9+87*6)-(-5*432-1)$
14BA	02446	$-123-4-5*-6*(78-9)+AB$	$BA9+876-5*43*2+1$
14BB	02447	$12-(3-45-678)+9AB$	$BA-(-987-654-3+21)$
1500	02448	$-12+3-(45-67)*(89-A)-B$	$-B-(-A98+76*-5)-(-4-321)$
1501	02449	$-12+3*(-4+56+7*(-8+9A)-B)$	$BA+9-8+7-6+5*(4+321)$
1502	02450	$1+234-5-67-89*(-A-B)$	$BA9+8*-7*(-6+5-4)+321$
1503	02451	$-12+3-45*-6*7+89+AB$	$BA9-87-(6*-54-321)$
1504	02452	$-1*-2*(34-56-(7-(89A-B)))$	$-B-(-A98-7)+654-3-21$
1505	02453	$1-(2+34*-5)-(-678+9A*-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6-54*-32*1$
1506	02454	$-1*2*(3+4-(5+6)-(-789+A*B))$	$B+A+9+8*(-76-(54-321))$
1507	02455	$-1-23+(-45-67)*-8+9AB$	$-B-(A-98-765+43*-21)$
1508	02456	$1+2+3+4*5*6+7+8+9A-B$	$-B+A98+76*5+4+321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1509	02457	-1+234-(5-678+9*-AB)	BA-987-6*(5+432)*-1
150A	02458	1+2*-3*(45+6)*-7+(8-9)*(A+B)	-B+A98-(-7-654)+3-21
150B	02459	1+234-5+678-9*-AB	BA9+8*7+65+432-1
1510	02460	1+2*-3-4*-5*(6+7)-89*(-A-B)	B+A98-7+654-3-21
1511	02461	1+2-(-3-45)*6*7-(-89+A-B)	-B-A9*(8-7)-65+432*1
1512	02462	-1+23-(-45-678-9AB)	BA9-8-7-(6-543)-2+1
1513	02463	1-(2-(345+6*78)-9AB)	BA+987+654-3-2-1
1514	02464	1+23+45-(-678-9AB)	BA9-8+7+6+543-21
1515	02465	1+2345+6-7*8-9AB	B+A+9+8-76*(5+4)*-3-(2+1)
1516	02466	1-2-34*(56-78)+9AB	BA9-8-7-6+543+2+1
1517	02467	1+2+345-(6*-78-9AB)	BA+987+654-(3-2)-1
1518	02468	-123+4*-56*(7-8-9)-(-A+B)	BA9+8+7-6+543-21
1519	02469	-1+2+3-45*(6+7)+9A*-B	-BA9+8*7-6-54*-3*21
151A	02470	1*(-23+45)*(67-(-8-9-A+B))	BA9-8*76*(5+4)-(-32+1)
151B	02471	-123+4-(-5*6*78-9+AB)	BA+987+654+3-2+1
1520	02472	-1*2*3*4*(-56+78-9A-B)	BA9-8-7+6+543-2-1
1521	02473	1234+5*6*7-8+9+A+B	BA+9-(87+6+54*-32+1)
1522	02474	1+2*(34+5)-(-678-9AB)	-B+A98+7+654*(3+2+1)
1523	02475	-1+2+34*-5*-6-7+89A+B	BA+9-87-(6+54*-32-1)
1524	02476	1234-5*6*7*(8-9+A-B)	BA9+8-7-6+543-(2+1)
1525	02477	-1+23*(4-5-6)*-7-(-8-9)*(-A-B)	-B+A9-8-7+6-54*(-32+1)
1526	02478	123-(-45-678)+9A*B	BA-9-8-7*-6*(5+43)+2-1
1527	02479	-1*(-2-3-(-4+56))*(78-(-9A-B))	BA9-8*(76-5+4)+32*1
1528	02480	-1234-5+6*-7*-89+AB	BA9+8+7+6+543-21
1529	02481	1*-234+5*6*(7+89)-AB	B+A98-7+654+3*2-1
152A	02482	123+4*-5*-6-7-8*9*-A+B	B-(A+9876-543*21)
152B	02483	12+34*-5*(-6-7)-(-8-9)*-AB	B-A9-8*-7*6+5*(-4+321)
1530	02484	1234+5+6*7*8+(9+A)*-B	BA-98*-7+6*5*-43*(-2+1)
1531	02485	1+2+34-56*(78-(9A+B))	BA-(-9+87)+6-(-54*32+1)
1532	02486	-1+2-34*-56-7-8-9-AB	B+A98-(7-654+3)-(-2+1)
1533	02487	1+2-3+4*567-8*-9*-A+B	BA9-8-76*(5-4)-3-21
1534	02488	-1+23+45*-6*-7+89+AB	BA9-8+7-(-6-543)-(-2-1)
1535	02489	12-3*(-4-5-678+9+AB)	BA9+876-5-4-321
1536	02490	1*(-2-3-4-(-5-(67+8)))*(9+A+B)	B-(-A98-(-7+654))-(-3-(-2+1))
1537	02491	12-34-56*7*8+9*-AB	BA-(-987-654-(-3+21))
1538	02492	-1-(-2345-(-6-7))-(-8+9AB)	B-A-98*(-76+5)-4321
1539	02493	-1-234*(-5-6)-(789-A+B)	-B+A9+8-7*-65-4*-321
153A	02494	1+2345-6-7-8-9AB	B+A98-7+654+3*2*1
153B	02495	-1+23*4+5+678+9AB	-B+A9-(-8-7+6+54*(-32+1))
1540	02496	1*2*3*(-45+67)*(8+9)-(-A+B))	BA9+8-(-7-(-6+543+2+1))
1541	02497	1*(2-3)*(45+67+89-A)*-B	BA+987+654+3+21
1542	02498	-12-34*-56-7+8-9A-B	BA+9+8-76*(-54+32)-1
1543	02499	-1*(234+5*-6*7-8+9)*(A-B)	BA9-(87-654+32)-1
1544	02500	-123+4+56*7-89*(-A-B)	BA9-(8+7-6-543-21)
1545	02501	123-45+678+9AB	BA9-87+654-32+1
1546	02502	1*-2*(-3+4)*(-5+6-(-7-(-89A+B)))	B-(-A+9876-543*21)
1547	02503	1+2+3*(-4+567)+8-(-9A+B)	B+A98*7+6*(-5-43)*21
1548	02504	-1+2345+6-7-8-9AB	B-(A+987-65*43+21)
1549	02505	-1*(-2345-6+7+8+9AB)	-BA-9-87+654*3-21
154A	02506	1+2345+6-7-8-9AB	BA9+87-(-65-432+1)
154B	02507	-1+2*-34*-5*6-7+8+9A-B	BA9+87+65+432*1
1550	02508	-1-(2+34*(5-67+8))-9A-B	-B+A98+7-(-654-3)+21
1551	02509	1-2*(3-4-5)*(67-(-8+9)+AB)	BA9+8-7*-6+543-21
1552	02510	1+2345-6-(-7-8+9AB)	BA9-87+6*(5+4-3)*21
1553	02511	1-2*-3*456+(7+89+A)*-B	B+A9-8*7-6+54*32+1
1554	02512	-1+23*(45-6)-(-789-AB)	BA+9-87+65*(4+3+21)
1555	02513	12-(3-45*(-67+8+9A))+B	-B+A*-98+(-7+654)*(3+2-1)
1556	02514	1-2*(-3-456)+789+A*B	BA9-8*-76-(-5-43)+21
1557	02515	1234+5-(-6-7*8*(9A+B))	BA9+876+5*4*(3-21)
1558	02516	1234-(567-(89A-B))	BA9-87+654+3-21
1559	02517	1-2-345-6*7*8*-9-A-B	-B-(-A98-7)-(-654-(32-1))
155A	02518	1+234*5+678+9*-A+B	BA9+876+5*4-321
155B	02519	1234+5-6*7*-8-9+AB	-B+A98+7+654+32+1
1560	02520	-1-(-2345-6-(-7-(-8+9AB)))	-B+A+9+876-5+43*21
1561	02521	-1+2*(-3+456)+789+AB	-BA-(-987+6+5-43*21)
1562	02522	1234-(5+678)+9AB	B-A-9+8+76+54*-32*-1
1563	02523	1-2345*(6-7)+8-9AB	-BA+9-87-(654*-3+21)
1564	02524	1+2345-6+7+8-9AB	B+A98-(-7-654+3-21)
1565	02525	1234-56-7*-8*9-(-A-B)	B-(-A-(-9-8)-(-76+54*32)+1)
1566	02526	1234+5-(-6*7*8-9A-B)	B+A98-(7-654-32*1)
1567	02527	-1+2+34*56+7+8-9A-B	B+A98-7+654+32+1
1568	02528	-1+2*-34*5*-6-(7-8)*9A+B	B-A-987-(65*-43-(-2+1))
1569	02529	1-2+(3+45+67-(-89A))*B	-B-A98*-7-654*-3*(-2-1)
156A	02530	1*(23-(45-6+78+9A))*-B	-B+A-(9-(87+6))+54*32-1
156B	02531	-1234-5*-6*7+8+9AB	-BA-(98-7+654*-3-2*-1)
1570	02532	1234+5-678+9AB	B+A98-(-76+5*(-4-321))
1571	02533	1+2+3*456-7*-89-AB	-B-A-(-987-6*54*3)-(-2-1)
1572	02534	123+4*-5+678+9AB	B-(A-987+6*(54*-3+2+1))
1573	02535	1*2345+6+7-(-8+9AB)	BA9-87-65*-4*3+2-1
1574	02536	1+2345+6+7-(-8+9AB)	BA+98+76*5-4*-321
1575	02537	12+3*4+5*-6*(-78+9)+A+B	BA9+8*(-7-(-65+4))-(-32+1)
1576	02538	1234-(567-89A-B)	-B+A98-7-(-6-5+43)*-21
1577	02539	-12-3-4*-5*6*7-8*(9-AB)	BA9-(87-654-3)+2*-1
1578	02540	-1+2+345+6*7*(-89+AB)	-B-A+98+7+6+54*32*1
1579	02541	1-2*(3-4-(-56-(78-9AB)))	-B-A*-98-(-7-654)+321
157A	02542	1*-23-(-4-56-7*(8+9)*(A+B))	BA9-(87-654-3-2)-1
157B	02543	1234-(5+67*-8+9+AB)	BA9-87+654+(-3-2)*-1
1580	02544	1234-5*-6-7-8-9-A*-B	BA9-87+654+3+2+1
1581	02545	123-4-5+678+9AB	-BA+9-87-654*-3-2-1
1582	02546	-12-34+5*6*7+89*(A+B)	-B-(-A9-87)-(-6-54*32-1)
1583	02547	1+234+567-(-8-9AB)	BA-(98-76)-(54*-32+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1584	02548	$1^*2^*(3-4)^*(5^*-6-789-AB)$	$BA-98+76-54^*-32^*1$
1585	02549	$12-3-45^*-6-7-(8+9)^*-AB$	$-BA-9+8-7^*-6^*54+3-(-2+1)$
1586	02550	$1+23^*45+67+89^*A-B$	$B-(A-98-7+6+54^*-32^*1)$
1587	02551	$-1^*(23-4^*5^*67-8-9^*-A^*-B)$	$BA9-8-7+654+3^*-21$
1588	02552	$1^*-2^*(3-4-(-5+6-(7-89A)+B))$	$B^*(A9+87)-654^*(3-2-1)$
1589	02553	$123+4-5+678+9AB$	$-B-A9-87+6^*(5+4+321)$
158A	02554	$1234+56^*7-89+AB$	$-B+A98+765-(43+21)$
158B	02555	$123-(4-5)+678+9AB$	$-B+A98+7+654+3^*21$
1590	02556	$12-3^*-45+678+9AB$	$BA9+87-6+543-21$
1591	02557	$1+2345-67-8-9A^*B$	$BA9+8^*-7+6^*(5+4-3)^*21$
1592	02558	$1+2345-(-6+78-9A^*-B)$	$-B+A9+8+7-(6+54^*-32)-1$
1593	02559	$1-(2+34^*-56)-(78+9-A-B)$	$BA9+8-(7^*-6-(543+21))$
1594	02560	$-1^*2^*(3-4-(5-6-7)-89A-B)$	$BA9-87+654-3+21$
1595	02561	$-1+234-(-567-8-9AB)$	$-BA+98+7^*6^*(54-3)+21$
1596	02562	$-1^*(-234-567-8-9AB)$	$BA9-(-876-54+321)$
1597	02563	$123+4+5-(-678-9AB)$	$-B^*(-A9-87-65+43+21)$
1598	02564	$1234-(-5-67^*8)-9A-B$	$B-(-A9+8+7-6-54^*32)+1$
1599	02565	$1+2345-(6-7^*8)-9AB$	$BA9-8+7+654+3^*-21$
159A	02566	$-1^*2^*(34-(5-6)-(789+AB))$	$BA9-(87-654)-(-3-21)$
159B	02567	$1-2-3^*(-456-78+9-AB)$	$BA9-8+76+543+2-1$
15A0	02568	$1^*(2-3)^*-456^*((7+8)^*9-AB)$	$B+A9-8+7^*(6-54)^*(-3-2-1)$
15A1	02569	$-12-34^*-5+678+9AB$	$BA9-8-(-76-543-2-1)$
15A2	02570	$-1+23+45^*(-67+8+9-A^*-B)$	$BA-9-(-8+7)^*6-54^*-32-1$
15A3	02571	$-1-234-5^*-6^*78+9+AB$	$B+A+9-(8-76+5)^*(-4+32-1)$
15A4	02572	$1+2-3^*(45-678)-(9+AB)$	$-B-A9-8-(-76+5)^*(4-(-3-21))$
15A5	02573	$123+4-56^*7^*-8+9A^*B$	$-B-A9-8^*(7-65^*4-32)+1$
15A6	02574	$-1^*2^*(34-(-5-6)+78)^*9^*(A-B)$	$BA-9^*-87+6^*5^*43-21$
15A7	02575	$-1+2-34^*-56-7-8^*-9-AB$	$BA9-87+654+32-1$
15A8	02576	$12^*(3-(4-56+7)-(-89-A-B))$	$B+A9^*8+7^*(-6-54-3)^*(-2-1)$
15A9	02577	$1+2345+6-7^*-8-9AB$	$BA9-87-(-654-(32+1))$
15AA	02578	$-12-34^*-56+78-9-AB$	$BA9-(-87+6)-(-543+2+1)$
15AB	02579	$1234+56^*7+8^*9-A-B$	$BA9+8+76+543-2-1$
15B0	02580	$-1+2345-67-89A-B$	$-B+A98+765-43+2-1$
15B1	02581	$1^*2345-67-89A-B$	$-B+A98-(-765+43)-2^*-1$
15B2	02582	$1+2345+6+7^*-8-9A^*B$	$B+A+98+7+6-54^*-32^*1$
15B3	02583	$1+2-(-3^*(-45+678)+9A)-B$	$BA-9-8-(-76+54^*(-32+1))$
15B4	02584	$-1+2345+67-8-9AB$	$BA9+87-6+543+2+1$
15B5	02585	$-1+234^*5+678-9+A-B$	$B^*(A+98+7+6-5+43^*2-1)$
15B6	02586	$-1+234^*5+678+9^*(A-B)$	$BA9+87-65^*(4+3^*2)^*-1$
15B7	02587	$1+234^*5+6+7-8^*-9A-B$	$BA9-8-7+654-(32+1)$
15B8	02588	$1+23^*-4+5^*(6+7^*-8-(9-A))^*-B$	$-B-A98-7^*-6+(5+4)^*321$
15B9	02589	$-1-2-34^*-56+78-9-AB$	$BA9-8-7-(-654+32)+1$
15BA	02590	$1^*(2-3)^*(4+56)^*(78-9A-B)$	$BA9+87-(-6-543)-(-2+1)$
15BB	02591	$-1-2^*-345+67^*8+9^*A^*B$	$BA9-(8-(76+543+21))$
1600	02592	$-1^*-23^*(-4+5)^*(-6-(-78-(9-A))+B)$	$BA9+87-(-6-543+2)+1$
1601	02593	$1+23^*(-45-(6-7-8)+9+AB)$	$-B+A98-(-765+4^*3+21)$
1602	02594	$-1234+5^*-6^*(-7-8-9-AB)$	$B-A-98-7^*(6+54-321)$
1603	02595	$-1-2-34+5^*6^*78+9-AB$	$-B+A98+765+4-32-1$
1604	02596	$1^*2^*(34-5^*6+7+89A+B)$	$-B^*(A-(-9+8^*(-7-6)+5))^*(-4-(-3+2-1))$
1605	02597	$-1-2+345-6-(-78-9)^*(A+B)$	$-B-(-A98-765-4)-32+1$
1606	02598	$1234-5+67^*-8-9^*-AB$	$-BA9+876-5^*-432-1$
1607	02599	$-1+2345-(6-78)-9AB$	$B+A98+765-43-2^*1$
1608	02600	$-1^*2^*(34-(56-7)-89A-B)$	$-BA9+8-7^*(6-5)^*(-432-1)$
1609	02601	$12-3^*(45-678)+9-AB$	$BA+9-8+76+54^*(32-1)$
160A	02602	$-1+2345-67-89A+B$	$BA9-(8-(7+654)+32^*1)$
160B	02603	$1234+5+6^*78-9+A-B$	$BA9-8+7+654-(32-1)$
1610	02604	$1+2345-(67+89A-B)$	$-B+A98+765-43+21$
1611	02605	$1+2345-6^*(-7-8)-9AB$	$-B+A98-(-765+4^*3^*2+1)$
1612	02606	$-12+345+678+9^*AB$	$B+A9+(-87-(-654+3))^*(2+1)$
1613	02607	$123+45+678+9AB$	$BA9-(-8-76)-(-543-21)$
1614	02608	$-1+2345-6^*7+8+9A^*B$	$BA9-(8+76^*-5+4-321)$
1615	02609	$-12+3-(45-67)^*89-A^*B$	$B-(-A98-765)-(-4+32+1)$
1616	02610	$1+2345+6^*-7+8-9A^*B$	$BA9-87-(6+5-43)^*21$
1617	02611	$-1+2345-(-6-78+9AB)$	$B+A9-(-87^*-6^*(5-(4+3))^*2+1)$
1618	02612	$-1^*-2^*(3-45-(67-8-9AB))$	$-B+A98+765+4+3-21$
1619	02613	$1-(-2345-(6+78)+9AB)$	$BA9-(-8+7+65^*-4^*3+21)$
161A	02614	$12+345-(6+(78+9)^*(-A-B))$	$BA9+8-7+654-3-21$
161B	02615	$-1^*(-2-3)^*(456+7-(89+A)-B)$	$-BA9-8-765^*-4-3-(2-1)$
1620	02616	$-1+234+5+67-89^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A98-7^*(-65-43-21)$
1621	02617	$-1234+5^*678-9A+B$	$-B+A98-(-765-4^*-3-(-2+1))$
1622	02618	$1+2^*(-34+56+7+89A)+B$	$BA9+87-(-6-(543+21))$
1623	02619	$1234-(-567+89)-AB$	$BA9+8+7-(-654+32-1)$
1624	02620	$1^*-2^*(3-4)^*(56+789+AB)$	$B-(-A98-765)-(-4+3+21)$
1625	02621	$-1+2-(-345-678)+9^*AB$	$-B-A-9^*8-7^*-6^*54+3-(-2+1)$
1626	02622	$-123+4^*(567-8+9^*-A)-B$	$-B+A9+8^*(7-(-65^*4-(-3+2)))-1$
1627	02623	$1-(-2-345-678+9^*AB)$	$BA-9876-543^*-21$
1628	02624	$-1^*-2^*(345+678-9A-B)$	$BA9-(8+7)-(-654+3-2+1)$
1629	02625	$-1-(-23+4^*5^*(-67+8))+9^*AB$	$B+A98-7^*-65+4^*321$
162A	02626	$-1-2345+6^*789+A^*B$	$B-(-A98-765)-(-4-3)-21$
162B	02627	$1-234^*-5-(-678-(9+A+B))$	$-B-(-A98-765-4-3^*-2+1)$
1630	02628	$1+2+34^*56+78-9A+B$	$BA9-(8+7-654-(3-2)-1)$
1631	02629	$-123-4^*(-567-(8-9A)-B)$	$-B-(-A98-(765+4)-(-3-2^*1))$
1632	02630	$1-2^*3^*-456-789-A^*B$	$-B+A9-8^*-76+54^*(3+21)$
1633	02631	$12-3-(45-67)^*89+A^*B$	$-B+A98-(-765+4-3)-2^*-1$
1634	02632	$1234+5^*67-8-9^*(-A-B)$	$BA9-(8-(-7+654)-(-3+2+1))$
1635	02633	$12-3^*(45-(678-9-(A+B)))$	$-BA9-8^*-7^*65+(4-32)^*-1$
1636	02634	$12-(-345-678+9^*-AB)$	$B+A98-(-765-(4+3))-21$
1637	02635	$1234-56+7^*8^*9+AB$	$B-A^*-98-7-6^*-5^*(43-2)+1$
1638	02636	$1234+56^*-7+8^*(9A+B)$	$BA-98-76^*(-5-(-4+3+21))$
1639	02637	$1-(-2+34^*-56-7^*(8-9)+A-B)$	$-BA-(9-8)-(-7-654^*3-2-1)$
163A	02638	$-123+45^*(67+89-AB)$	$BA9-8-(-765+4^*32^*1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
163B	02639	$1 - (-234 - 56^* - 7^* (89 + A^* - B))$	$BA9 - (8 - 7) - (-654 - (-3 - 2^* - 1))$
1640	02640	$1^* - 2^* (-34 - 5^* (-6 + 78 - 9A))^{* - B}$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 - (-654 + 3) + 2 - 1$
1641	02641	$-12 - 34^* - 56 - 78 + 9A - B$	$-B - A9 - 8 + 7 + 654^* + 3 + 2^* - 1$
1642	02642	$12 + 3^* - 4^* (-5 - 6 + 7 - 89 - A^* B)$	$-BA - (-987 - 654) + 321$
1643	02643	$1234 - 567 - (8 + 9A)^* - B$	$B + A98 + 765 - 4 - 3 - 2^* 1$
1644	02644	$-1^* (-2 + 34^* - 56 - 7 - (89 - A^* B))$	$BA9 + 8 - (7 + 6)^* (5 - 43 - 21)$
1645	02645	$-1 - 23 - 4567 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-B - A9 - 8 - (-7 - 654^* 3) + 2^* 1$
1646	02646	$12 - (3 - 4) - 5^* 6^* - 78 - 9A - B$	$-B - (A9 + 8) - (-7 - 654^* 3) - (-2 - 1)$
1647	02647	$-1 + 2345 - 6 + (7 - 8 + 9A)^* - B$	$-BA9 - 8 - 765^* - 4 + 3 + 21$
1648	02648	$1^* - 2^* (-3 - 45 + 6 + 7 - 89A - B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 + 654 - 3 + 21$
1649	02649	$-1 + 2345 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9A^* - B$	$-BA + 9 - 8 - 76^* (-5 - 4 - (-3 + 21))$
164A	02650	$-12 + 3^* 456 + 7 + 8^* - 9^* - A + B$	$B + A98 - (-765 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$
164B	02651	$1 + 2^* 345^* - 6 + 7^* (-8 + 9A)^* B$	$B - A - 98 + 7 - 654^* - 3 - 21$
1650	02652	$1234 + 567 + 8^* - 9 - AB$	$-BA + 9 - 8 - 7^* (-6 + 54 - 321)$
1651	02653	$1 - 2^* - 3^* (4 - 56 + 7^* 8^* 9^* (-A + B))$	$BA - 9 + (-87 - 65)^* (-4 - 3)^* - 2^* - 1$
1652	02654	$-12 + 3^* 456 + 7^* (89 - A + B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 + 654 + 3 + 21$
1653	02655	$1 - 2^* - 3456 - (-78^* - 9 - A)^* B$	$-BA9 - 8^* (-7 - 6)^* (54 + 3 - 21)$
1654	02656	$1 + 2 + 34^* 56 - 7 - (-8 - (-9 + A) - B)$	$BA9 - (-8 - 7) + 654 + 3 - (2 + 1)$
1655	02657	$-1 - (2 - 34^* - 5 + (67 - 89)^* - A^* - B)$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 3 + 2^* - 1$
1656	02658	$-1 + 2345 + 6 - 7 - 89A - B$	$BA9 - (-8 - 7) - (-654 - 3 + 2 - 1)$
1657	02659	$1 - 23 + 4 + 5^* - 6^* - 78 + 9^* - A + B$	$-B - (-A9 - 87) + 6 + 54^* 32^* 1$
1658	02660	$-1 + 2345 - 6 + 7 - 89A - B$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 + 4^* 3^* - 21$
1659	02661	$-1 + 23^* 456 + (-7 - 89)^* AB$	$BA9 - (-8 - 7 - 654 - 3 + 2^* - 1)$
165A	02662	$1234 + 5 - 6^* (-7 - 89 + A) - B$	$B^* (A + 987 + 6^* 5^* - 43)^* 2^* - 1$
165B	02663	$-1 + 2345 - 6 - (78 - 9^* - AB)$	$B - (A - 9) - (-87^* (65 - 43) + 21)$
1660	02664	$-1234 + 5^* (678 + 9 - A - B)$	$B - A9 - (-8 + 7) - 654^* - 3 - 2 - 1$
1661	02665	$1 + 2345 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9A^* B$	$-B + A98 - (-765 - (-4 + 32) - 1)$
1662	02666	$-1 + 2^* - 3 - 4567 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$B - A + 9^* (87 - 6) + 54^* (3 + 21)$
1663	02667	$-1 + 23 - (-4^* - 5^* - 67 + 89^* - A) + B$	$B - A9 + 876 - 543^* - 2 + 1$
1664	02668	$-1^* (2 + 345 - 6^* - 7^* 8^* - 9 - AB)$	$BA9 - 8^* - 7 - 65^* - 4^* 3 - 21$
1665	02669	$12 + 34^* 56 - 78 + 9A - B$	$BA9 + 87 - (-654 + 3^* 21)$
1666	02670	$1 + 2345 - 6 - 7 - 89A + B$	$B + A98 + 765 - 4 - 3 + 21$
1667	02671	$1234 + 5 + 6 + 7^* 89 - AB$	$-B + A98 + 765 + 4 + 32 - 1$
1668	02672	$-1 + 2345 - (-6 - 7 + 89A) - B$	$-BA + 98^* 7 + 65^* (43 - 21)$
1669	02673	$1^* (2 - 3)^* (4567 - 8^* 9A^* B)$	$B^* (-A + 98 + 76 - (5 - 43 - 2) - 1)$
166A	02674	$1 + 2345 + 6 + 7 - (89A + B)$	$-BA9 + 8 + 765^* 4 + 32 + 1$
166B	02675	$-1 - 2 + 345^* 6 - 78 - 9 - AB$	$BA9 + 876 + 5^* - 43 - 21$
1670	02676	$1 - (-2345 + 67) - 8 + 9^* - AB$	$B + A98 + 765 - 4 + 3 + 21$
1671	02677	$1 + 23 - (4 - 5^* - 6^* - 78) - (9A - B)$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 + 654 - (-32 + 1)$
1672	02678	$-1 + 2 + 34^* 56 - (78 - 9A - B)$	$B - (-A98 - 765) - (-43 + 21)$
1673	02679	$-1 + 2 - 345^* - 6 - (78 + 9) - AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 + 654 + 32 + 1$
1674	02680	$-1 - (-2345 - 6) - 7 - (89A - B)$	$B + A - 98 - 7 + 654^* 3 - 2^* 1$
1675	02681	$12 - 34^* - 56 - (-7 - 8 + 9 - A - B)$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 654 + 32 + 1$
1676	02682	$1 + 2345 + 6 - 7 - 89A + B$	$B + A98 + 76 - (54^* - 32 - 1)$
1677	02683	$-12 - 3 + 456 + (7 - 89)^* (-A - B)$	$-B + A98 + 765 + 43 - 2^* - 1$
1678	02684	$1^* 23 + 4 + 5^* - 6^* - 78 - 9A + B$	$B + A98 + 765 - (-4 - 3) + 21$
1679	02685	$-1 - 2 + 34^* 56 - 78 + 9 + AB$	$B + A + 9^* (-87 + 6 - (54 - 321))$
167A	02686	$-1^* (-2 + 3^* (-45 - 6 + 7))^* (8 + 9^* (-A + B))$	$-BA + 9^* 87^* (6 + 5) - 4321$
167B	02687	$12 + 3^* (-45 - (-678 - 9 + A) - B)$	$B + A98 + 765 - 4 + 32 + 1$
1680	02688	$-12^* (-34 + 5 - (-67 - (-89 - AB)))$	$-B + A - 9 + 8^* (76 - 5)^* 4 + 3 - 21$
1681	02689	$1 - 2 - 345^* - 6 + (-7 - (-8 - 9) + A)^* - B$	$B + A98 + 765 - 4^* - 3 + 21$
1682	02690	$12 + 3 - 4567 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-B - A - 9 + 87 - 65^* (4 - 32) - 1$
1683	02691	$-1 + 2 + 3^* 45^* - 67 + 89AB$	$BA + 98 - (-7 + 6 + 54^* - 32^* 1)$
1684	02692	$1234 - 567 + 8 + 9AB$	$B - A9 + 8 - 7 - 654^* - 3 + 21$
1685	02693	$1 + 2 - 34 - 5^* (-67 + 89)^* (-A - B)$	$B + A98 - (-765 - 4 - 32) - 1$
1686	02694	$-1 + 2345 - (-6 - 7 - (-89A + B))$	$B - (-A98 - 765) + 4 - 32^* - 1$
1687	02695	$1 - 2 - 345^* - 6 - 78 + 9 - AB$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 32 + 1$
1688	02696	$1 - (-2345 - 6) - (-7 + 89A - B)$	$BA - (-987 + 6^* - 54^* 3) + 2 + 1$
1689	02697	$1234 - 56 - 78^* - 9 - AB$	$B - A9 - 8^* - 7 + 654^* 3 - 21$
168A	02698	$-1 + 2 + 3^* - 45^* - 6 + (78 - 9)^* (A + B)$	$-BA^* (9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5 + 4 - 3 + 21))$
168B	02699	$-1 + 2345 - 6 - 7^* 8 + 9^* - AB$	$BA9 - (-876 - 5^* - 43 + 2 - 1)$
1690	02700	$1 - 23^* - 45 - (6 - (-7 + 89A + B))$	$B + A98 + 765 + 43 - (2 + 1)$
1691	02701	$1 + 23 - (4567 - 8^* 9A^* B)$	$BA9 - 8 - (7 - 654) + 3^* 21$
1692	02702	$-1 - (-2345 - 6 + 789 + AB)$	$B + A98 + 765 + 43 - 2 + 1$
1693	02703	$1234 - (-5 + 67^* - 8 - 9 - (-A + B))$	$B - A + 98 - (-76 + 54^* (-32 - 1))$
1694	02704	$-1 + 2 - 3^* 45^* (-6 - 7 - (-8 - (9 - A) + B))$	$B + A98 - (-765 - (43 + 2) + 1)$
1695	02705	$-123 - (-456 - 7) - (-8 - 9)^* AB$	$-BA - 9^* (-8 + 7 - 65)^* 4 + 32 + 1$
1696	02706	$-1^* 2^* (34 + 5 + 6 + 7^* - 8 - 9A)^* B$	$B + A98 + 765 - (-43 - 2 - 1)$
1697	02707	$1234 + 567 - (8 + 9 + AB)$	$BA9 + 87 + 654 - 32 + 1$
1698	02708	$-1234 + 56^* 78 + 9A^* - B$	$-B - (-A + 9 + 8) - (-7^* 6^* 54 + 32^* - 1)$
1699	02709	$1 + 2 - 3^* (-45 - 678 + 9A - B)$	$-B + A98 + 765 + 4 + 3^* 21$
169A	02710	$-1 + 2 - 34^* (-56 - 78 - 9^* - A) - B$	$B - A + 9^* 87 + (-65 - 4)^* (3 - 21)$
169B	02711	$-1 - (-2345 - 6 + 7^* 8) + 9^* - AB$	$BA9 - 8 - (-765 + 4) - 3^* 21$
16A0	02712	$1^* - 2^* (-3 - 4 - 56 + 7 + 8 + 9A^* - B)$	$B - A - (-9 - 8 + 7^* 6^* - 54 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
16A1	02713	$-1234 + 5^* 678 - (-9 + A)^* B$	$B - (A9 + 8) - (-7^* - 6^* (-54 - 3) - 21)$
16A2	02714	$-123 - 4 - (-5^* - 6^* - 78 - 9A - B)$	$BA9 - 8 + 765 - (43 + 21)$
16A3	02715	$-1 + 234 + 5 + 678 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 + 654 - 3^* - 21$
16A4	02716	$1^* 234 + 5 + 678 + 9AB$	$BA9 - (-87 - (654 - 3) + 21)$
16A5	02717	$1 - 2^* (-34 - (56 - 7) - 89A + B)$	$-B^* (A9 + 8^* (-76 - 5 - (-43 - (-2 - 1))))$
16A6	02718	$1234 + 567 - (8 + 9A) - B$	$-B + A98 - (7 - 6^* 5)^* 43^* (2 - 1)$
16A7	02719	$-1 - 2 + 34^* 56 + 78 - 9 + A - B$	$B - A9 - (8^* - 7 - 654^* 3 + 2 + 1)$
16A8	02720	$-1^* 2^* (-345 + 6^* 78 - 9AB)$	$B - A9 - (87 + 6 - 5^* - 4)^* (3 - 21)$
16A9	02721	$1 - 2^* 34^* 5 - (6 + 7)^* 8^* (-9 - A - B)$	$B + A + 9^* 8 + 7^* - 6^* - 54 - 32^* 1$
16AA	02722	$1^* - 2^* (34 - (56 - 78 + 9AB))$	$BA9 - (-87 - 654 - 3 + 21)$
16AB	02723	$1234 + 567 - (-8 + 9 + AB)$	$-BA - (98 + 76 - 5^* 432 - 1)$
16B0	02724	$1234 - (56 + 7 + 8^* 9^* - A) + B$	$BA9 + 87^* 6 - (54 - 321)$
16B1	02725	$1234 + 567 - 8 + 9 - AB$	$-B + A98 - (76 + 5 - 43^* 21)$
16B2	02726	$-123 - 45^* - 67 + 8 - 9A^* B$	$BA - 98 - 76^* (5 + 4 - 32 - 1)$
16B3	02727	$1 + 234 - 56^* - 7^* 8 - 9A^* B$	$B - A9 + 87 + 6^* (-5 + 4)^* - 321$
16B4	02728	$1234 + 567 - (8 + 9 - A^* - B)$	$B + A98 + 765 + 43 + 21$
16B5	02729	$1234 + 567 - 89 - A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 87 + 654^* 3 - 21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
16B6	02730	$1 - (-2345+6-78+9A*B)$	$BA9+8 - (-765+43+21)$
16B7	02731	$-1+234*5+6*7* (-89+AB)$	$-B - (-A98-765-43*2+1)$
16B8	02732	$-1+2345-6* (-7-8)+9A*-B$	$-BA - (9+87*-6) -5*(4-321)$
16B9	02733	$-123+4-5*6*-78+9+AB$	$B - (A9-87+6*(-5+4-321))$
16BA	02734	$1234+567+8-9A-B$	$BA-9-8*-7*6+5*(-4+321)$
16BB	02735	$-1-2345+6*789 - (-A+B)$	$BA9 - (-8-765-4)+3*-21$
1700	02736	$123*-4*(-56+78-9-A-B)$	$BA9-8 - (-765 - (-43-2))+1$
1701	02737	$1-2345-6*-789+A-B$	$BA9+87+654-3*2-1$
1702	02738	$1-2+345+678+9A*B$	$BA9-8+765 - (43+2-1)$
1703	02739	$-12-3+(45-67)* (-89 - (-A+B))$	$-B*(A-98-76-5-43+2+1)$
1704	02740	$1234 - (-567+8+9A-B)$	$BA9 - (-87-654) -3 - (-2-1)$
1705	02741	$1234+567 - (-8-9+AB)$	$BA9-8+765-43-2*-1$
1706	02742	$-1+2*(-34-56)*-7+89A-B$	$BA9-8 - (-765+43-2)+1$
1707	02743	$12+34+56*7+(8+9)*AB$	$B-A9*-8 - (-765-432-1)$
1708	02744	$1*2*(345-6-7*(-8-9A)+B)$	$BA9+87+654+3-2-1$
1709	02745	$12-34*-56+7+89-A-B$	$B+A9*-8-7*(65-432-1)$
170A	02746	$-1+2*(3 - (-456-7)+8)+9AB$	$BA9 - (-87-654-3 - (-2+1))$
170B	02747	$12+3*456-78*-9-A-B$	$BA9 - (8 - (765-4)+32) -1$
1710	02748	$1*2*(34+5-6-78+9AB)$	$BA9+87 - (-654 - (3+2-1))$
1711	02749	$1234+567 - (89-A+B)$	$BA9 - (8-765) -4-32+1$
1712	02750	$1234+567+89*(A-B)$	$-B*A*(9+8 - (7+6) -5+4*-3*2*1)$
1713	02751	$1+2+3*(-4+567 - (8-9A-B))$	$BA9+87+654+3*2+1$
1714	02752	$-1 - (-2345-6+7) -8-9*AB$	$BA9+8+765-43 - (2+1)$
1715	02753	$1*-234+5*-67*-8 - (-9*-A-B)$	$B-A9-876+(5+4)*321$
1716	02754	$1-234+5*-67*-8+9*-A+B$	$-BA-9-8+765+4*321$
1717	02755	$-12+3*-4*-5 - (-6-7-8)*(9A+B)$	$BA9-8+765+4-32-1$
1718	02756	$1234+567+8-9A+B$	$BA9 - (-8-765+43 - (2-1))$
1719	02757	$12+3*(4 - (-567 - (89A))) -B$	$BA9 - (8-765-4+32-1)$
171A	02758	$1+2345-6-7+8-9*AB$	$BA9-8 - (-765+4) -3-21$
171B	02759	$-1-2 - (-34*5+(6+7+8))*(9-A))$	$-B+A*(98+76-5+43+21)$
1720	02760	$-1+2345+67-89A+B$	$BA9+876+54*-3-2-1$
1721	02761	$1*2345+67-89A+B$	$B*(A+98+7+65+4+32-1)$
1722	02762	$1+2345+67 - (89A-B)$	$-BA+987-6*-5*43-21$
1723	02763	$-1+2+34*56+78+9 - (-A-B)$	$-B-A+987+654+321$
1724	02764	$-1*-2*(-34*-5*6-7*(89-AB))$	$-BA9+8 - (7-6*(543-21))$
1725	02765	$1+(-2+3*4)*(5+6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8+765-4-32+1$
1726	02766	$-1 - (-2345-6) - (-7+8+9*AB)$	$-BA - (9-876+(54+3)*-21)$
1727	02767	$1234+56-7*8*-9+AB$	$-B+A-9*(-8+7)+654*3-21$
1728	02768	$1 - (-2+3-45*67) - (-8+9AB)$	$-B-A+9-8+7-654*-3 - (2+1)$
1729	02769	$1234+5+6 - (7+8*-9*A) -B$	$BA9+8+765-4*3-21$
172A	02770	$-1-23*-45-67-8+9AB$	$B - (-A+9+8-7-654*3+21)$
172B	02771	$1234+567-89+A+B$	$BA9 - (-8-765) - (-4+32) -1$
1730	02772	$1 - (-2345+6-7-8-9*-AB)$	$BA9 - (-87-654-3-21)$
1731	02773	$1-23*-45+6 - (78-9AB)$	$BA9 - (-8-765) - (-4+32-1)$
1732	02774	$1-23+4*(567+8 - (9A-B))$	$BA9 - (-8 - (765-4-3-21))$
1733	02775	$-1-2-3*(45*6-789-AB)$	$B-A-9*8*76+5432*1$
1734	02776	$-12+3*(4-56)*(78-9A+B)$	$BA9 - (876-5*(4+321))$
1735	02777	$12-34*-56-7+8-9+AB$	$BA98-7*65*(-4 - (-32+1))$
1736	02778	$12-3-45*(-67 - (-8-9-A))+B$	$-B-A98 - (765*-4+(3+2)*-1)$
1737	02779	$-1-234 - (-5+6*7)*(-89+A+B)$	$BA9-87*-6-5-4+321$
1738	02780	$1*(-2+3)*4*(567-89 - (A-B))$	$BA9+8+765-43+21$
1739	02781	$1-2-345*-6-7+8-9A-B$	$BA9-8+765+4*-3 - (-2-1)$
173A	02782	$-1-2*34*-5+678+9AB$	$-B+A98+(-765-4*32)*-1$
173B	02783	$1-23+45*(67+89-AB)$	$B*(A9 - (-87+6*-5) -4 - (-3*-2-1))$
1740	02784	$1-2*-34*5+678+9AB$	$-B+A98+7+65*-4*(-3-2+1)$
1741	02785	$1-23*-4*5+(6-78-9A)*-B$	$B-A+987+654+321$
1742	02786	$12*(3-4-5+6+78+9A-B)$	$BA9-8+765-4+3-2-1$
1743	02787	$1234+5+6*(7-8-9+AB)$	$BA9-8+765-4+3-2*1$
1744	02788	$-1*-2*(3+45+67+89A-B)$	$-BA+987+6*-5*-43 - (-2+1)$
1745	02789	$-123+4*(567-8*-9-AB)$	$BA9+87*6+5-4+321$
1746	02790	$1*2*(34-5+67+89A+B)$	$-B-A+9*-8*-7-6-543*(-2-1)$
1747	02791	$1234-5*(-6+7 - (8 - (-9-AB)))$	$BA9-8+765-4+3*2-1$
1748	02792	$1*-2*(-3-45+67+8-9AB)$	$BA9-8+765-4+3+2+1$
1749	02793	$12+34*56+7 - (8-9)+AB$	$-BA - (-987+6)+543*-2*-1$
174A	02794	$-1*(-23 - (45+67+89-A))*B$	$BA9 - (8-765) - (-4+3) - (-2-1)$
174B	02795	$1*2+(3^4*5*6)*7-8+9A-B$	$-B-A98-765*-4-3+21$
1750	02796	$1234+567+8*9-AB$	$BA9+8 - (-765+4+3+2+1)$
1751	02797	$1+2345 - (6*-7+8) -9*AB$	$B-A98 - (-765*4 - (3-2))+1$
1752	02798	$1234 - (56-7*(-8 - (9-AB)))$	$-BA9-87+6*(-543+2)*-1$
1753	02799	$1+234*5+6*(78-9A+AB)$	$-B-A9-8-7*(-6*54-32+1)$
1754	02800	$1*-2*(3-4)*(-56-7*(-8-9-A-B))$	$BA9+8+765-4-3+2-1$
1755	02801	$-1-2*(3-4)*(56-78+9AB)$	$BA9+8-76*(5+4+3)*(-2+1)$
1756	02802	$-1-2-3*(45-6-789+AB)$	$BA9 - (-8-765+4) - (-3+2+1)$
1757	02803	$-1-2-3-45*(-67-89+AB)$	$B-A9+8+765-4*-321$
1758	02804	$-1+23*45-6*(7-89-AB)$	$BA9+8+765+4-3-2-1$
1759	02805	$-12-345*-6-7-89+A+B$	$B+A+987+654+321$
175A	02806	$1*(-23+4)*(5-6)*(7+8 - (-9A+B))$	$-B+A98-76*(-5-4-3-2)+1$
175B	02807	$-1-2345-6*(-789-A)+B$	$BA - (-9+87) -654*-3-21$
1760	02808	$-1+2*(3+456) - (-78-9AB)$	$BA9-87-65-43*-21$
1761	02809	$1 - (-23+4*-56*7) - (-8*9A+B)$	$-BA9-87+6*543-2+1$
1762	02810	$-1234-5*(-678+9)+AB$	$BA+9+8-7*6*-54-32+1$
1763	02811	$1+2+34-5*-6*78+9A-B$	$-B-A-9-8*-7 - (-654*3-2+1)$
1764	02812	$-1+2345+6-789 - (A+B)$	$BA9 - (-876-5-4*(-32+1))$
1765	02813	$1-2*(3+4+5-6 - (-7 - (8-9AB)))$	$-B-A9*-8-7*(65+43)*2*-1$
1766	02814	$1 - (-2345-6+789A) -B$	$BA9-8 - (-765+4 - (3+21))$
1767	02815	$-12-345*-6-78 - (9-A)*B$	$B+A9*(-8-7*6) -5432*-1$
1768	02816	$-12-345*-6-78-9 - (-A-B)$	$B*(A+9 - (-87-6+54))*(3 - (-2+1))$
1769	02817	$1234+567 - (8+9A)-B$	$BA-9-87+654*3+2+1$
176A	02818	$-1*-2*(-3-45+67 - (-8-9A))*B$	$-BA - (98-7) - (6+5*(-432-1))$
176B	02819	$1-2+(345+67)*(-89-A*-B)$	$-BA-98*7+65*(-43+2)*-1$
1770	02820	$-1+2345-6-789+A-B$	$-B-A9-87-6 - (5*-432+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1771	02821	$-12 \cdot 3^*(4+5) \cdot (-67+89-AB)$	$B \cdot A9^* - 8 \cdot (76^* - 5^*4 - 3) - 21$
1772	02822	$1+2345 \cdot 6 \cdot (789 - A+B)$	$-BA9 \cdot 87 \cdot 6^* \cdot (-543 \cdot 2^*1)$
1773	02823	$1-234 \cdot 5^*67^* \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$BA9 \cdot 8+765 \cdot (4 \cdot 32+1)$
1774	02824	$1+2345 \cdot 6 \cdot (789+A)+B$	$BA9 \cdot 8+765 \cdot 4+32^*1$
1775	02825	$1-234^* \cdot 5 \cdot (-6 \cdot 7) \cdot 8 \cdot 9^* \cdot AB$	$BA9+876+5^* \cdot (-43+21)$
1776	02826	$-1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot 3^* \cdot (4 \cdot 5) \cdot (-678+9AB)$	$BA9 \cdot 8^* \cdot 76 \cdot 54+321$
1777	02827	$-1234+56^*78 \cdot 9^*AB$	$B+A \cdot (9 \cdot 8^*7)+654^*3 \cdot 21$
1778	02828	$-1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (-3 \cdot (-4+5))+6 \cdot (7 \cdot (-8+9AB))$	$-B+A98+7+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 43^* \cdot 21$
1779	02829	$1234+567 \cdot (-89+AB)$	$BA+9 \cdot (87+654^* \cdot 3) \cdot (-2+1)$
177A	02830	$-1+2345 \cdot 6 \cdot 78^* \cdot (-9+A+B)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5^* \cdot (4 \cdot 3) \cdot 21$
177B	02831	$1+2^*34^*5^* \cdot 6^* \cdot 7+89A^* \cdot B$	$BA9 \cdot 8+765 \cdot (-4 \cdot 32+1)$
1780	02832	$1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (-34 \cdot (-56+7)) \cdot (8+9AB)$	$BA9+8+765+43 \cdot 21$
1781	02833	$1234+567 \cdot (-8+9+A+B)$	$-BA+9^* \cdot 87 \cdot 65^* \cdot 43 \cdot 21$
1782	02834	$-1+2345+6 \cdot 789 \cdot A+B$	$-B \cdot A9 \cdot (87 \cdot 6) \cdot 5^*432+1$
1783	02835	$1234 \cdot (-567+8)+9 \cdot A \cdot B$	$-BA9 \cdot 87+6^*543+21$
1784	02836	$-1 \cdot 23^* \cdot 45^* \cdot 6^* \cdot 7 \cdot 8^* \cdot 9AB$	$-BA98 \cdot 76^*5^* \cdot (-43 \cdot (2 \cdot 1))$
1785	02837	$-123+4+567+89^*(A+B)$	$B \cdot A^* \cdot 987 \cdot 6543 \cdot 21$
1786	02838	$1234 \cdot 5+6 \cdot 7^* \cdot (8 \cdot 9A)+B$	$BA9 \cdot 8 \cdot (-765 \cdot 43 \cdot (-2 \cdot 1))$
1787	02839	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 34+5^*6^*78 \cdot (9 \cdot AB)$	$-BA+9 \cdot (8+76+5^*432^* \cdot 1)$
1788	02840	$-1+2 \cdot 34^* \cdot 56+78+9A \cdot B$	$-BA^*(9 \cdot 8)^*(7 \cdot (6+5))^*(4 \cdot 3+2)^* \cdot -1$
1789	02841	$1234+5^* \cdot (-67+89+AB)$	$-BA+9 \cdot 87 \cdot (65+4)^* \cdot 32 \cdot 1$
178A	02842	$12+345^*6 \cdot 78 \cdot (-9+A \cdot B)$	$BA \cdot 98+7 \cdot 654^* \cdot 3+21$
178B	02843	$1 \cdot 234^* \cdot 5 \cdot 67+89A+B$	$B \cdot A9 \cdot (87+6+5^* \cdot 432^*1)$
1790	02844	$-1 \cdot (-2345 \cdot (-678 \cdot 9)) \cdot AB$	$BA9 \cdot 8+765+43 \cdot (-2 \cdot 1)$
1791	02845	$-123 \cdot 4 \cdot 5^*67^* \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot AB$	$-B \cdot A9+8^*76 \cdot 5^* \cdot (4 \cdot 321)$
1792	02846	$1+2345 \cdot 678 \cdot (9+AB)$	$B+A98 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5) \cdot 43^*21$
1793	02847	$-1+2345 \cdot (6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9^*AB$	$-B \cdot A^* \cdot 98 \cdot (-765 \cdot 432+1)$
1794	02848	$1234 \cdot 5^*67+8+9^*AB$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5+43^* \cdot 2^*1$
1795	02849	$-1+2^*3+4 \cdot 5^*(67 \cdot 8)^* \cdot (-9 \cdot (A \cdot B))$	$BA9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 765 \cdot 4) \cdot (-32 \cdot 1)$
1796	02850	$1234+567+89 \cdot A^*B$	$BA9+876+5^* \cdot (-4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2+1)$
1797	02851	$-12+3 \cdot (-456+7) \cdot (8+9)^* \cdot AB$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7+6)^*5+4^*(3^*2+1)$
1798	02852	$1-23^*(45 \cdot 6) \cdot (7 \cdot (-89 \cdot A)^* \cdot B)$	$B+A \cdot 98 \cdot 7^* \cdot (-6^*54 \cdot 32+1)$
1799	02853	$-1+2+3+(-45+67)^* \cdot (8+9A) \cdot B$	$BA9+876 \cdot 54+32^* \cdot 1$
179A	02854	$-12+345+678+9AB$	$BA9+876 \cdot (54+32 \cdot 1)$
179B	02855	$1234 \cdot (-567 \cdot (8 \cdot 9 \cdot A))+B$	$-BA+9 \cdot 87^*6^* \cdot 5+43^* \cdot 2^*1$
17A0	02856	$-12^* \cdot 3^* \cdot (4+5^*6)^* \cdot (7+89+A^* \cdot B)$	$B+A98 \cdot 7^*65+4^*321$
17A1	02857	$1+2345 \cdot 678 \cdot 9A \cdot B$	$BA9+8+765 \cdot 43^* \cdot (-2+1)$
17A2	02858	$1234+567 \cdot 8+ (9 \cdot A)^* \cdot B$	$BA9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 765 \cdot 43 \cdot 2) \cdot 1$
17A3	02859	$-12+345^*6 \cdot (-78 \cdot (-9A \cdot B))$	$BA9 \cdot 8+7^*65+432+1$
17A4	02860	$1234+567 \cdot 89 \cdot A^* \cdot B$	$BA9+8 \cdot (-765 \cdot 43 \cdot 2 \cdot 1)$
17A5	02861	$-1+2 \cdot 34 \cdot 5^* \cdot 6^*78+9+AB$	$-B \cdot (A \cdot 98) \cdot (-7+654^* \cdot 3) \cdot 21$
17A6	02862	$-1+2345 \cdot 678+9 \cdot AB$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5+4^* \cdot (3 \cdot 21)$
17A7	02863	$1-234 \cdot 5^* \cdot 67^*8+9 \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$B \cdot (-A \cdot 98) \cdot (-7^*6^*54+32^* \cdot 1)$
17A8	02864	$1+2^*(345 \cdot (-678+9)) \cdot (-A+B)$	$B+A^*987 \cdot 6543 \cdot 2^* \cdot 1$
17A9	02865	$1234+5+6+7^* \cdot (-8 \cdot 9+AB)$	$-B+A^*987 \cdot 6543+21$
17AA	02866	$-12+345^*6+78+9 \cdot AB$	$BA9 \cdot 8 \cdot (-765 \cdot 43)+21$
17AB	02867	$1234 \cdot 5+678 \cdot (9+AB)$	$BA \cdot 9 \cdot 8^* \cdot 7^* \cdot 6 \cdot 5^*432^* \cdot 1$
17B0	02868	$1+2345 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 89^*A \cdot B$	$BA+9 \cdot 8+7^* \cdot 6^* \cdot 54+32 \cdot 1$
17B1	02869	$-1+2 \cdot (-345 \cdot 678 \cdot 9AB)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 54+3 \cdot 21$
17B2	02870	$-12+3 \cdot (-45^*67+8) \cdot 9A^*B$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5^* \cdot 4^* \cdot 3 \cdot 21$
17B3	02871	$1-2^*(34+5)^*(67 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot A \cdot B)$	$BA+98+7^* \cdot 65^* \cdot 4+321$
17B4	02872	$1^*2^*(3 \cdot 4+5+6+7 \cdot 8+9AB)$	$BA9 \cdot 876^*5+4321$
17B5	02873	$-1+2 \cdot 34^* \cdot 56+78 \cdot (-9 \cdot AB)$	$-BA9 \cdot (8+7)+6^*543 \cdot 21$
17B6	02874	$-1+2+345^*6+78 \cdot 9A \cdot B$	$BA9 \cdot (-876+5+43+21)$
17B7	02875	$1234+567+8 \cdot 9+A+B$	$-B \cdot A9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^*6 \cdot 5^* \cdot (-432+1)$
17B8	02876	$12+345^*6+78 \cdot 9 \cdot AB$	$BA \cdot 9+8 \cdot 7+6^*(5 \cdot 4)^*321$
17B9	02877	$-1+2345 \cdot 678 \cdot (9A \cdot B)$	$B \cdot (-A+9) \cdot (-8^*7+654^* \cdot 3) \cdot 21$
17BA	02878	$1234 \cdot 5+678 \cdot 9A \cdot B$	$-B+A9 \cdot (-8+7+654^* \cdot 3) \cdot 21$
17BB	02879	$1+2345 \cdot 678 \cdot 9A+B$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5+4+3^* \cdot 21$
1800	02880	$-1+2345 \cdot 6 \cdot (-7+89^*A+B)$	$B+A \cdot 98 \cdot 76 \cdot 5^* \cdot (-432+1)$
1801	02881	$1234 \cdot (-567+89)+AB$	$BA9+876+5 \cdot 4+3^* \cdot 21$
1802	02882	$12+345+678+9AB$	$BA9+8+7+6^*54^*3+2^*1$
1803	02883	$-1 \cdot (-2345 \cdot (-678+9 \cdot A^*B))$	$B+A \cdot 9^* \cdot 8 \cdot 76^* \cdot (-5 \cdot 43+21)$
1804	02884	$-12^*(3+4 \cdot 5+6 \cdot (-7+89 \cdot A^* \cdot B))$	$BA9+876+5 \cdot 43 \cdot 21$
1805	02885	$1234 \cdot (5 \cdot 678) \cdot (-9+AB)$	$-BA \cdot 9^* \cdot 87 \cdot (-65 \cdot 4 \cdot 3)^*21$
1806	02886	$12 \cdot 34^* \cdot 56+78+9+AB$	$BA9 \cdot (-876+54) \cdot (-3+2^*1)$
1807	02887	$-12+345^*6+7 \cdot 8 \cdot (9+A \cdot B)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 54 \cdot 3 \cdot 2+1$
1808	02888	$1234+5 \cdot (-678+9A+B)$	$BA+9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^*(5 \cdot (4+321))$
1809	02889	$-1^* \cdot 23^*(45+6 \cdot 78+9+AB)$	$-BA9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^* \cdot 543 \cdot 21$
180A	02890	$-1 \cdot (-2 \cdot 3^*45^*6) \cdot (7+8)^* \cdot (-9A \cdot B)$	$-B+A98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65+43^* \cdot 21)$
180B	02891	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 34^*(56 \cdot 7)+89 \cdot AB$	$B \cdot A \cdot (9 \cdot 8 \cdot 765) \cdot 4^* \cdot 321$
1810	02892	$-1+2345 \cdot (-6 \cdot 7)+89^* \cdot A \cdot B$	$BA9+876+(54 \cdot 3+2)^* \cdot 1$
1811	02893	$1234+567+8+9+A+B$	$BA \cdot 9 \cdot (8+7) \cdot (654 \cdot 3)^* \cdot (-2 \cdot 1)$
1812	02894	$1+2345 \cdot (-6 \cdot 7) \cdot (89^*A+B)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 54+3^*(2 \cdot 1)$
1813	02895	$1234 \cdot (-5 \cdot (678+9)) \cdot AB$	$BA9 \cdot (-876+54 \cdot 3) \cdot (-2+1)$
1814	02896	$-123+45^*67 \cdot 8^*(9+AB)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 5 \cdot (43+2+1)$
1815	02897	$12+3+4^*56^*7+8^*(9A+B)$	$BA9+876 \cdot 54+3+2+1$
1816	02898	$1234+5 \cdot (-678+9 \cdot A^* \cdot B)$	$B \cdot (A9+8^*(7+65 \cdot 4 \cdot 321))$
1817	02899	$1-2+(34+5)^*(67 \cdot (8+9)) \cdot A^* \cdot B$	$-BA9 \cdot 8^*7^* \cdot 65+4^*3^*21$
1818	02900	$1234 \cdot 5+678 \cdot 9A+B$	$BA9 \cdot (-876 \cdot (-5 \cdot 43+2)) \cdot -1$
1819	02901	$1-2 \wedge (3+4)+5+6^*7^*8^*9+A \cdot B$	$-B \cdot (-A9 \cdot 876 \cdot 543^*2) \cdot -1$
181A	02902	$-1 \cdot 2+345^*6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8+9 \cdot A+B$	$-BA \cdot 98+76 \cdot 5^* \cdot 432^*1$
181B	02903	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3^*(4 \cdot (5+678)) \cdot (-9+A)+B$	$-BA+9+87^* \cdot 6^* \cdot 5 \cdot (43+2+1)$
1820	02904	$-1^*(2+3)^*4^*56^*(7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot (-A+B))$	$-B \cdot (-A \cdot 987 \cdot 6) \cdot 5^* \cdot 4^* \cdot 3^* \cdot 21$
1821	02905	$-1 \cdot (-2345+678) \cdot 9^*A+B$	$-B+A98+76 \cdot 5 \cdot 43^* \cdot 21$
1822	02906	$1234+567 \cdot 8^* \cdot 9 \cdot A \cdot B$	$BA9 \cdot (-876 \cdot 5) \cdot 43 \cdot (2+1)$
1823	02907	$1-2+3^*456+789 \cdot AB$	$BA9 \cdot (-876+5) \cdot (-4+32+1)$
1824	02908	$-1234 \cdot (5+6^*78^* \cdot 9) \cdot A+B$	$BA9+876+5 \cdot 43 \cdot (-2 \cdot 1)$
1825	02909	$-1234 \cdot 567^* \cdot 8 \cdot 9AB$	$BA9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 765+43^* \cdot 2 \cdot 1)$
1826	02910	$1^* \cdot 2^*345^*(6 \cdot 7+8 \cdot (9 \cdot A+B))$	$BA9+876 \cdot (-5+43 \cdot 2) \cdot -1$
1827	02911	$1+2+3^*456+789 \cdot AB$	$BA9+8 \cdot (76 \cdot (5 \cdot 43^* \cdot 21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1828	02912	$-12 * (-34 - 56 - (78 + 9 - A) - B)$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 - 65 - 43 * -21$
1829	02913	$1 - (-23 + 4 - 5 * 6 * 78 - (9A + B))$	$BA9 + 876 - 54 - 3 + 21$
182A	02914	$1234 + 567 + 8 * -9 + AB$	$-BA - 9 - 87 * -6 * 5 - (4 - 3) * 21$
182B	02915	$1234 + 5 - 67 + 8 * 9A - B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 - 32 - 1$
1830	02916	$1 + 2345 + 6 + 7 - 89 * A + B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 - 32 * 1$
1831	02917	$1 * 2^{\wedge}(3 + 4) + 5 * (6 + 7 * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - (9 + 8 - 765) - 4 * -321$
1832	02918	$1234 + 56 - (-7 - 8 + 9) * AB$	$-B + A9 - (-8 - 7 - 654 * 3 - (2 - 1))$
1833	02919	$-1 + 23 - 4 * 56 * -7 + (89 - A) * B$	$BA9 + 876 - 54 + 3 + 21$
1834	02920	$1234 + 5 * -67 - (-89A + B)$	$BA - 9 + (-8 - 7) * (6 - 54 * 3) - 2 - 1$
1835	02921	$-123 - 4 * (-567 - 89 + AB)$	$B + A + 9 * 8 * 7 * 6 + 5 - 4 * 3 * 2 - 1$
1836	02922	$-1 * -2 * (345 - 6 + 789 - AB)$	$-B + A9 + 87 + (-65 + 4) * (-32 + 1)$
1837	02923	$12 + 3 - (-45 * 67 - (-89A - B))$	$-B - (-A98 + 7) - (-654 - 321)$
1838	02924	$-1 * -2 * (345 - 6 + 7 + 8 * (-9 + AB))$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 - (4 - (3 - 21))$
1839	02925	$12 - 34 * (-5 - 67 + 8) - 9A - B$	$BA9 + 876 - (-5 - 4) - (32 + 1)$
183A	02926	$1234 - 5 - 6 * 78 + 9AB$	$B + A98 + 7 + 65 + 43 * 21$
183B	02927	$1234 + 567 - 8 * 9 * (A - B)$	$BA9 + 876 * (5 - 4) - 3 - 21$
1840	02928	$-1 * -2 * (3 + 4 - 5) * 6 * (-7 + 8) * (-9 + AB)$	$BA9 - (-876 - 5) - (4 + 3) - 21$
1841	02929	$12 + 3 - 4 * (5 - 6) * -7 * (-89 - (A - B))$	$BA9 + 876 - 54 + 32 * 1$
1842	02930	$1 + 2345 - (67 + 8 * 9A) + B$	$BA + 9 * -87 - 6 * (-5 - 432) + 1$
1843	02931	$1234 + 5 - (-67 - 8) * (9 - A + B)$	$BA - 9 + 87 + 65 * (-4 + 32 + 1)$
1844	02932	$-1 + 23 + 45 * 67 - 89A - B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 + 3 - 21$
1845	02933	$-12 + 345 * 6 - 78 + 9A + B$	$B + A - (98 - 76) * (-5 - 43) * -2 * -1$
1846	02934	$1 - 23 - 4 * -567 - 89 - AB$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 - 43 + 21$
1847	02935	$-12 - 3 + 456 - (-78 - 9A) * B$	$BA9 - (-876 - 5 * -4) - (3 - 2 - 1)$
1848	02936	$12 + 34 * (56 + 7) - 8 + 9 - A + B$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 + 4 - 3 - 21$
1849	02937	$1234 + 56 - 7 * (-8 - (9A - B))$	$-B + A98 + 7 + 654 + 321$
184A	02938	$1 - 2 * (34 - 567) - 8 + 9AB$	$B + A - 98 - 7 * 6 - 5 * (-432 - 1)$
184B	02939	$1234 + 567 + 89 - A - B$	$BA - 98 + 765 - 4 * -321$
1850	02940	$1234 - 56 + 7 + 8 * 9A - B$	$-BA + 9 * 8 * -7 * -6 + 54 - 3 - 2 - 1$
1851	02941	$1 + 2 * 34 * -5 * (-6 + 7 - 8) + 9 + AB$	$BA - (9 + 8) + 7 - (-654 * 3 - 21)$
1852	02942	$1234 - 5 * 67 - (-89A - B)$	$-B + A9 + 8 - (-7 + 654 * -3) + 21$
1853	02943	$1234 - (-567 + 8 * (9 - A) * B)$	$BA9 - 8 + 765 - 43 * (-2 - 1)$
1854	02944	$-12 - 34 * (-56 - 7) + 8 - (-9 - A) + B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 * -432 * 1$
1855	02945	$1 + 2345 + 6 - 789 - A * -B$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 * (-432 - 1)$
1856	02946	$1 * -2 * (-345 - 6 - (789 - AB))$	$BA + 98 + 7 * -6 * 54 * (-3 - 2 * -1)$
1857	02947	$-1 - 23 + 4 * (567 - 8) + 9 * (-A - B)$	$BA9 - (-876 - (5 - 4 * -3 - 21))$
1858	02948	$1 - 2 - 3 + 456 - (-78 - 9A) * B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 - (4 - (3 - 2 + 1))$
1859	02949	$-12 + 3 + 4 * 567 - 89 - AB$	$BA9 + 876 - (5 - 4) - 3 * 2 + 1$
185A	02950	$1 + 2 - (-345 * 6 + 78) - (-9A - B)$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
185B	02951	$1234 + 567 - 8 * (9 - A - B)$	$BA9 - (-876 + 5) - 4 - (3 * -2 + 1)$
1860	02952	$-1 + 2345 - 6 - 789 + AB$	$B + A + 987 - 6 * -5 * 43 - 2 * -1$
1861	02953	$-1 * (-2345 - (-6 - 789) - AB)$	$-B + A - 98 + 7 - 6 + 5 * 432 - 1$
1862	02954	$1234 + 567 - 8 + 9A - B$	$B - (-A - 98 + 7 * 6 * (-54 - 3) - (2 + 1))$
1863	02955	$1 * 2345 - 678 - 9 - A - B$	$BA + 987 + 6 + 54 * (-3 + 21)$
1864	02956	$1 * -2 * (34 - 5 + 6 - 78 - 9AB)$	$B + A - (-987 + 6 - 543 * -2 * -1)$
1865	02957	$1 - 2 - 345 * -6 - 78 + 9A + AB$	$B - A9 + 876 + 5 - 4 * -321$
1866	02958	$-1 - 2 * (-34 - 567) + 89A + B$	$BA9 - (-8 - 765) - 4 * 32 * -1$
1867	02959	$1234 + 567 + 89 + A - B$	$B + A98 + 7 + 654 + 321$
1868	02960	$1234 + 5 - (-6 + 7 * (-8 - 9A)) + B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$
1869	02961	$1234 + 567 + 89 - A + B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 - 4 * -3 - 2 + 1$
186A	02962	$12 + 3 * (456 - 78) + 9A * B$	$BA9 - 87 + 65 - 43 * -21$
186B	02963	$-1 + 2 + 3 - (45 + 6 + 78 + 9A) * -B$	$BA9 - (-876 + 5 * 4) - (-3 - 21)$
1870	02964	$1234 + 567 + 8 - 9A * B$	$B - A - (9 + 87 - 6 - (5 * 432 - 1))$
1871	02965	$-1 - 2 * -3 + 4 * 567 - 89 - AB$	$BA9 + 876 - (-5 - 4) + 3 + 2 * -1$
1872	02966	$1 + 2345 + 6 - 789 + AB$	$BA9 + 876 - 54 - 3 * -21$
1873	02967	$-1 - 2 * (-34 - 567) - 8 + 9A * B$	$BA9 - 876 + 54 * (32 + 1)$
1874	02968	$1 + 2345 - 6 + (7 - 89 + A) * B$	$B + A - (-987 - 6) - 543 * -2 * 1$
1875	02969	$1234 - 56 - (7 - 8 * (-9 + AB))$	$-B - A * (-98 - 76 - 54 - 3 - 21)$
1876	02970	$1234 + 567 - (-8 - 9A + B)$	$-B * (-A9 - 8 - 7 - 6 * 5 - 4 * (32 + 1))$
1877	02971	$-1 + 23 + 4 + 5 * -6 * (7 - 89) - A + B$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 * (4 - 3 + 2) + 1$
1878	02972	$123 + 45 * 67 - (8 + 9A) * B$	$BA9 - 8 * (-76 - 54 - 3) + 2 + 1$
1879	02973	$1 * 2345 - 678 - (-9 + A + B)$	$BA9 + 876 + 5 + 4 * -3 + 21$
187A	02974	$-1 + 2345 - 678 - 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 876 - (-5 - 4 * 3 + 2 * -1)$
187B	02975	$-1 + 2345 - 678 - 9 * (-A + B)$	$BA + 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 * 3 + 21$
1880	02976	$1 + 2345 - (678 + 9) - (-A + B)$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 - 3 + 21$
1881	02977	$1234 - 5 + 678 - 9 - A - B$	$B - (-A98 + 76) + 5 * -4 * 3 * -21$
1882	02978	$1 + 2 - 3 * (-4 + 5) * -678 + 9A - B$	$-B + A + (-9 + 8) * 76 - 5 * 432 - 1$
1883	02979	$-1 - 234 * -5 - 67 - 8 + 9AB$	$-B - A * (-9 + 8) - 76 - 5 * -432 * 1$
1884	02980	$-1 + 2345 - (-67 + 89 * A) + B$	$-B + A9 + 87 + 654 * 3 - 21$
1885	02981	$1234 + 567 - (-89 - A) + B$	$B * (A - 98 - 7 - (65 - 4 - 321))$
1886	02982	$-12 * (-3 - 45 + 67 - 89 - AB)$	$BA9 + 876 + 54 - 32 + 1$
1887	02983	$1234 - 56 + 7 + 8 * (-9 + AB)$	$B + A - (98 - 7 - 6 - 5 * (432 - 1))$
1888	02984	$-1 * 2 * (-3 + 4) * (-56 - (7 - 8 + 9AB))$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 76 - 5 * -432 * 1$
1889	02985	$1234 - (-567 - 8 + 9 - AB)$	$BA9 - (-876 + 5 + 4 - (32 + 1))$
188A	02986	$1 * -2 * (-34 + 56 - (78 + 9AB))$	$BA9 + 876 - (-5 - 43 + 21)$
188B	02987	$1234 - (-567 + 8) - (-9 - AB)$	$-BA - 98 * (7 - 6 * 5) - (-4 - 321)$
1890	02988	$-12 + 3 - 4 * 5 * -67 - 8 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 - 43 * -21$
1891	02989	$1234 - 56 + 7 - 8 - 9 * -A * B$	$-BA9 - 8 - 76 + 54 * 3 * 21$
1892	02990	$1 + 2 * 34 * -56 - (-78 * 9 * A + B)$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 * (54 + 321)$
1893	02991	$1234 - 56 - 7 + 8 - 9 * A * -B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 4 + 32 - 1$
1894	02992	$-1 + 2345 - 678 - (-9 - (A - B))$	$BA9 - (-876 - (5 + 4 + 3)) + 21$
1895	02993	$-1 + 2345 - 678 - 9 * (A - B)$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 - (-4 - 32) + 1$
1896	02994	$-1 - (-2345 + 678 - 9) - A + B$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 * 65 + 4 * 321$
1897	02995	$1 + 2345 - 678 - 9 * (A - B)$	$BA9 - 87 + 654 + 321$
1898	02996	$1 - (-2345 + 6 + 7 - 8 * -9A) + B$	$B - A + 9 + 8 * -76 * -5 + 432 * -1$
1899	02997	$1 * 2345 - 678 - (9 - A) + B$	$BA9 + 876 - (-54 - 3) - 21$
189A	02998	$1 + 2345 - 678 - 9 + A + B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 + 43 - 2 - 1$
189B	02999	$-1 * (23 + 4 - 5 - (6 * 7 * -8 * -9 - (A - B)))$	$B - A * -98 - 76 * 5 * -4 + 3 + 21$
18A0	03000	$1 + 2345 - (-6 - 7) + 8 * -9A - B$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 6 - (-5 + 43 * -21)$
18A1	03001	$1 - 23 - 4 + 5 * -67 * -8 - 9A - B$	$BA9 + 876 - 5 - 43 * (-2 + 1)$
18A2	03002	$-1 + 2 - 34 + 5 * 67 * 8 - 9 - A * B$	$-BA - 9 - 8 + 76 - 5 * -432 + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
18A3	03003	1234-56+789+A*-B	B-A-9*8*-7*6-(5*4+3-2+1)
18A4	03004	1234-5-6-(78*-9-AB)	BA9+876-5-(-43-(2+1))
18A5	03005	-1+2345-67-8*(9A-B)	BA-98-76-5*-432-1
18A6	03006	-1+2345-(-6+7)-(-8*-9A-B)	-B+A-9-8*(7-(-65+4)-321)
18A7	03007	1234+5+678-9+A-B	-BA+98-7*6-5*(-432-1)
18A8	03008	1234-5*6+789-AB	-B-A-(-9+8*7-6-5*-432*-1)
18A9	03009	-123-45*6*(-7+8*(-9+A)-B)	BA9+876+5+43+2*-1
18AA	03010	1*2*(-3-(-456-7*89)+AB)	BA9+876-(-5-43+2)+1
18AB	03011	12-3+45*67-8+9*-AB	B-A*9+87*(-6+5+4-3-2+1)
18B0	03012	1-2*(-345-678)+9A+B	-B-(A9+8-76+5*-432*1)
18B1	03013	-1-2+345*6+7-8+9A-B	BA9+876+5+43-2*-1
18B2	03014	-1-(-2345+678-9-A-B)	BA9+87-65-43*-21
18B3	03015	1234-(-5-678-(9A)+B)	B-A-9-87+6*(54+321)
18B4	03016	1-(-2345+678-9-A-B)	-BA9-8*-7*(65-(-4-3))+21
18B5	03017	-123-4*(-567-8+9+A+B)	-BA-(9-(8+76-5*-432*1))
18B6	03018	-1+2+345*6-7-(8+9-AB)	BA9+876-(-54+3)-2*-1
18B7	03019	1234-5+6+7+8*9A+B	BA9+876+54-3+2+1
18B8	03020	-1-(-2345-6-7-8*-9A)+B	-BA+9+8*76+54*32+1
18B9	03021	-12-345*-6-7-(8-9-AB)	BA9-(-876-54)-(-3+2)+1
18BA	03022	1-(2-345*6)+7-(-89-(-A+B))	BA9+876+(-54-3)*(-2+1)
18BB	03023	1234+5+6*-7*8+9A*B	-BA-9+8+7+(65+4)*(32+1)
1900	03024	1*(-2+34-56)*(7-8-9A+B)	BA9-8*-765-4321
1901	03025	1234+5-(-678-9-(A-B))	B+A+9*-8*-7*6+5*4*(-3+2)*1
1902	03026	1+2+3-4*(5+67)*8-9AB	BA9+876-5+43+21
1903	03027	1234-5-6-(-789+AB)	BA-9*-8*-7*-6-5+3*-21
1904	03028	-1+2*345+67*8+9AB	-B-(-A-98-765)-4*-321
1905	03029	1234-(-5-678+9)-(-A-B)	-B-A9-(-8-76+5*-432)+1
1906	03030	-1*-2*(3+4-5-6+7+8+9AB)	B-A*98*7+6543*(2-1)
1907	03031	1-2-(3+4*(-567+8))-9A-B	-BA+9+87+6*5*-43*-2+1
1908	03032	12+3+4*567+(-8-9)*A-B	-BA+98-(7+6+5*-432-1)
1909	03033	1-23+4*567-8-9A-B	BA+98-7-654*-3-2*1
190A	03034	1-(234-5*-6*(-7-89))-A+B	BA+98-(7-654*3+2-1)
190B	03035	12-(3-4*(567-8)+9+AB)	B-A9+8-7*6*-54+321
1910	03036	1*-2*(-34-56+7+8-9AB)	BA9+876+5-(-43-21)
1911	03037	1234+5-6+789-AB	-B+A9*8+(7+65)*-4*3*2*-1
1912	03038	1+2345-6+78-9*A*B	BA9+876-5+4*(-3+21)
1913	03039	1234+56*-7+8+9AB	BA9+876-(-5-4-3*21)
1914	03040	1*-2*(3-4)*(-5+6-(-78-9AB))	-B-A9+87-(-6+5*-432-1)
1915	03041	1-23-(45*-67+8*(9+AB))	-BA9+87+6*543+21
1916	03042	-1+2+3+45*67+8+9*-AB	BA9+8*-7+654+321
1917	03043	-123+4+56-(7+8+9)*-AB	-B+A98+76-54*(3-21)
1918	03044	-12-(-3+4*-567+8*(9A)+B)	-BA+98+7-6-(-5*432+1)
1919	03045	-1+2-(34*(5-67)-89+A+B)	BA-9-(-87-654*3)+21
191A	03046	1234-5*-6*(7-89+AB)	-B+A98+7-(-6+5*-4*-3*-21)
191B	03047	-1+2-3-4+5*-67*-8-9A+B	BA9-(-876-54)+3+21
1920	03048	1-2-3*-456-7*8-9*-AB	B-(A9+87*6*5)-(-43-21)
1921	03049	1234+5+6-(-789+AB)	-B-A+9+8-7+6*5*-43*-2*1
1922	03050	-1*(-2-3)*(-456-7+89A-B)	-B-A*9-8*-76-(54*-32+1)
1923	03051	1-2+3-45*6*(7-8-9)-AB	BA9+876-5-43*-2-1
1924	03052	12*(-3-(4-(5+6)-(78-9+AB)))	BA9+876-5+43*-2*-1
1925	03053	-12-3*4+(-56+78)*9A+B	-BA9+8-7*6+54*3*21
1926	03054	-1*-2*(34*-56+789)*(A-B)	-B+A98*(76-54)+32+1
1927	03055	-1+2-345*-6+7+8+9A+B	-B-A+98*76+5-4321
1928	03056	1234+56+7*(-8+9+AB)	BA+9-8+765-4*-321
1929	03057	-1-23-4*-567+8-(9-A*-B)	-BA+9*(8+7)-6-5*432*-1
192A	03058	-12-3+456*7+8-9AB	BA9+876-(-54-32-1)
192B	03059	12+3*-4+(56-78)*-9A-B	-BA+9+87*-6*-5-43*-2*1
1930	03060	1234-(-5-6-789-A*-B)	-BA9-8*-7*65+4+321
1931	03061	-12-3456+7*89A+B	B+A9+8+765-4*-321
1932	03062	-1*-2*(-3-(-4-5))-(-6-78-9AB))	BA9+876+5+43*-2*-1
1933	03063	1+2+3*4*5*(67-8-(-9+AB))	-B-A+9-(-876-5+4*-321)
1934	03064	-123+456*7-89A+B	BA9-8-(-7-65+43*-21)
1935	03065	123-4+5+6*-7*-8*9-AB	-B+A*(-9+876)+5432*-1
1936	03066	12-3*4-5*(67-8)*-9-AB	-B+A9+8-7*6*5*(-4-3)*-2*-1
1937	03067	1+2+345*6+7*(-8+9+A+B)	-B-A-9-(87-(-65-43)*-21)
1938	03068	-123-4*(-567-8)*(-9A)+B	B-(A+9)+8-7-(-6+5*-432+1)
1939	03069	1+2+(-3+45-67)*-89+A+B	B+A-9-8*7*65+4321
193A	03070	1+23+4*(567-8)+9-AB	-B+A9*-8-(-7+6)*(5+4)*321
193B	03071	-1-2+3*(-45+678+9A)+B	BA9-8-7*6+54*(-3+21)
1940	03072	-1-2-3456+7*89A+B	BA+9+8+765-4*-321
1941	03073	-1+2-3+456*7+8-9AB	-B+A9+876-(-5+4*-321)
1942	03074	12-3*-456-(-789-(A+B))	-B+A98-7-6+543*-2*-1
1943	03075	-1-2+3+456*7+8-9AB	BA9+876-5*4*3*2*1
1944	03076	12-3+4*567+(-8-9)*AB	-BA+98-(765-43)*(-2-1)
1945	03077	1+2345+6+7*(-8-9A)+B	B+A-(9-876)-(-5-4*321)
1946	03078	1234+5-(-6+78-(9-A))*-B)	-BA-9-(-87+6*(-54-321))
1947	03079	1-2-3+4+(-56-78)*-9A+B	B+A98+7-6*5*-43-21
1948	03080	-1-(-23-4)-(-5*-6*(-7+89)+A*-B)	-B*(A-(-9-876)-543*2+1)
1949	03081	12+3*-4-(-56-78)*9A+B	BA9+8-(-76+5+43*-21)
194A	03082	1234-56+78-9*-A*B	BA-98-7-6-5*-432-1
194B	03083	-12+34-(-56+78)*-9A-B	BA9-8-76*5+4*321
1950	03084	1-23-(4+5*6)-(-7+8+9)*-AB	-BA+987-6+5+4*321
1951	03085	-1+2345-678+9*A+B	BA9-(-876-5*(43-21))
1952	03086	1234-5*(-67-89)-A*-B	-B-(-A-9-8-(-7+6)-5*432-1)
1953	03087	1+23-(-456*7-(-8-9AB))	B-A*(9-876)+5432*-1
1954	03088	1+2-3+4*(567+8)-9-AB	B+A*(-9+876)-5432+1
1955	03089	-1-2-345*-6-7*(89-AB)	BA+987+6+543*-2*-1
1956	03090	1-2-(345+6-78-9A)*-B	-B+A9-87-(-6-5*432+1)
1957	03091	1234+567+89+AB	BA9+8+76+5-43*-21
1958	03092	1234-56-(-789-(-A-B))	BA9+87+6-5-43*-21
1959	03093	1+2345-(-678-9A+B)	-B+A98-(-7-6*5*43)+21

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
195A	03094	$1 * (-23+45) * (-6-7-8-(-9-AB))$	$BA9+876+54+3*21$
195B	03095	$-1-2*345-67-89*(-A-B)$	$-BA-9-8-765*(-4+3-2)-1$
1960	03096	$-1+23-4*-567-(89+A+B)$	$BA-98+7-6-5*-432-1$
1961	03097	$-1-(-2345-6)+7-8*(9A-B)$	$BA9-8+7+654+321$
1962	03098	$1+2*(34+567)-(8-9AB)$	$B-A-9*8-7*-65-4*-321$
1963	03099	$1+2345+6*7*8-9*AB$	$B-A98-7-6*-543+21$
1964	03100	$1-23*(-45+6)-(-7-8)*(-9+AB)$	$-BA-987-654*(-3-2)+1$
1965	03101	$-1+2-(-3+4*-567-8+9A-B)$	$BA9+87*6+543-(2-1)$
1966	03102	$1234+5-(67-8*(9+AB))$	$BA9+876-5-4*32*-1$
1967	03103	$-1+23+45+6*-7*8*-9*(-A+B)$	$BA9+87*6+543+2-1$
1968	03104	$1234-56-78*(9-A-B)$	$BA9-87-6+5*4*-3*-21$
1969	03105	$-1*-23*(-45-67+8+9)*(A-B)$	$-BA+987-65*4*-3*2*1$
196A	03106	$1234-5+67-8*(9-AB)$	$BA9+8+765+4*3*21$
196B	03107	$-1*(-2345+678-(-9+AB))$	$B-A+9-87-(-65-43)*21$
1970	03108	$1+2345-(678+9-AB)$	$-BA+987+(654-3)*2+1$
1971	03109	$1-(-2+3*-456)-(-7-8+9*-AB)$	$B+A98-7+6-543*2+1$
1972	03110	$12+3*(-45-(-678-9A)+B)$	$-BA-987+6*543+21$
1973	03111	$1+234+(56-78)*(-9A+B)$	$B-A9+87-6*(-54-321)$
1974	03112	$1234-56+789+A-B$	$BA9+876-(5-4*-32)*-1$
1975	03113	$1234-56-789*(A-B)$	$-B*(A-9)*(876+(-54+3)*21)$
1976	03114	$1234-(-56-789)-AB$	$-B-A-9+87*6*5+43+2+1$
1977	03115	$1+2345-678-(-9A-B)$	$-BA+987+6*5-4*-321$
1978	03116	$1*2*(34+5-6+78+9AB)$	$BA9-87+6+5*4*-3*-21$
1979	03117	$-1+2-3-(4+56*(7*-8+9))-(A+B)$	$-BA+9+8+7-65*(-4-32)+1$
197A	03118	$1*2*(-3-45*-6+789+AB)$	$B+A-98-(76-5*432)+1$
197B	03119	$1-2+34-(5*-67+89+A)*B$	$-B-(A-9)-(87-65*(4+32*1))$
1980	03120	$1*(-2+3-45)*(6-(-7+8*9))-(-A+B)$	$BA9+876-5*(4-32+1)$
1981	03121	$1234-(-56-7+8)-9*A*-B$	$BA9-8*(-76-54+3-21)$
1982	03122	$1-23*4-5*-6*(-7+89+A)-B$	$BA9-(-876+54*-3)-21$
1983	03123	$1234+5-6+7-89*-A+B$	$B-(-A98-7-6)-(543*-2-1)$
1984	03124	$-1-(-2345+678)-(-9-AB)$	$BA*(9-8)*(-7+65-43+2+1)$
1985	03125	$1234-5+6+7+89*A+B$	$-BA9+8+7*(65+432-1)$
1986	03126	$1-(-2345-(-678+9+AB))$	$BA9-8+7+6+54*(-3+21)$
1987	03127	$-1*(-2+3)*45*(-67-(-8+9-(A+B)))$	$B+A9+8-76+5*432-1$
1988	03128	$-12+345*6-(-78-9-AB)$	$B+A9+8-76-5*432*-1$
1989	03129	$1234-(-5-678+9-AB)$	$-B-(A-987+65)+4*321$
198A	03130	$1-(-23+45-6*-7*-8*9-AB)$	$BA9-8+(-7+6-(5+43))*-21$
198B	03131	$123-4*5*(6*-7-89+A-B)$	$-B+A*-98-765*-4-32*1$
1990	03132	$-1*23*(-4+56+7*-8+9-AB)$	$-BA-9-8-(-765-4*3)*(2+1)$
1991	03133	$1+23*4*(56-(-78+9A+B))$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5*(4+3-2)-1$
1992	03134	$1234-(-56-789-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5*(4+3-2/1)$
1993	03135	$-12-3*-456+789-A*-B$	$-BA-(-98-76)+5*432+1$
1994	03136	$1234-(-5-678-(9A+B))$	$B+A+98*-7-65*-43*(2-1)$
1995	03137	$1234-5-6+789-A-B$	$BA-98-7*-6-5*-432-1$
1996	03138	$12+3+4*(567+8)-9A+B$	$BA-(98-7*6-5*-432*-1)$
1997	03139	$1234+5-(-678+9-AB)$	$-B-A+9-8*-76+54*32-1$
1998	03140	$1*2*(34+5+67+8+9AB)$	$-B-A*-9*(-8+7)*(-65+4+32)+1$
1999	03141	$1-2*3+(45-67)*(8-9-A)*B$	$-B-A+9-(8-76)-(5*-432-1)$
199A	03142	$1234+5-6-78-9*-AB$	$-B+A9+8*(7+6+5)*(4+3)*(2+1)$
199B	03143	$1234-5-67-(-8-9*AB)$	$-B-A98-76+54*-3*-21$
19A0	03144	$1*2*3*(45-678+9AB)$	$BA9-(-876-54*3*(-2-1))$
19A1	03145	$-1-(-2-3*-4*-56)-(-7-89)*(A+B)$	$BA9-87-6+543*2-1$
19A2	03146	$1234+5+678-(-9A-B)$	$B*(A-98-7+6-54+321)$
19A3	03147	$-1-23-4*-567*(-8+9)-A-B$	$BA9-87-6-543*-2+1$
19A4	03148	$12+3-45*(6-78)-9AB$	$BA-9-8*7+6-5*(-432+1)$
19A5	03149	$1234-5+6-(-789+A)-B$	$-BA+9-8-(-7-6)*5*43-21$
19A6	03150	$1-23+4-5*-67*8-9-(-A-B)$	$BA+98*(7+6)-5*4*3*-21$
19A7	03151	$-123+4*567+89+A+B$	$B+A-(-9*87-(-6-54)*-32)-1$
19A8	03152	$1234+567+(-8-9-A)*-B$	$BA+98*(76-54)+3*2*-1$
19A9	03153	$1234+5-6*-7*(-89+AB)$	$B+A+98*(76-54-(-3+2))*1$
19AA	03154	$1*-234+5*678-9A*B$	$B+A-9-87*6*5-(-43-2+1)$
19AB	03155	$1-234*-5+67+8+9AB$	$B+A+9-8+7-6*(-54-321)$
19B0	03156	$1*(-2+3-4)*(5-678-9*A-B)$	$-B+A9-87*-6*5-43-(-2-1)$
19B1	03157	$1234+5+678+9+AB$	$B*(-A+9+8)*(76-(-5+43+2+1))$
19B2	03158	$1234-5-6-789*(A-B)$	$BA+98*(-7+6+54-32+1)$
19B3	03159	$-12-3+4*567-8+9-A-B$	$BA-98+7+6*(54+321)$
19B4	03160	$1*(-2-3)*(4-(-567+8+9AB))$	$-B-A-98+7*(654-321)$
19B5	03161	$1-2*(-3+4)*(56+78)*(-9+A-B)$	$B-A+9-(8-76-5*432+1)$
19B6	03162	$12-(-3-4*567-8*-9-A-B)$	$-BA9-8*-76*5-43*-21$
19B7	03163	$-1-(-2345-67)+8*(-9A+B)$	$B-(-A9+87)-6*(-54-321)$
19B8	03164	$1-234+5*-6*(-7-89)+AB$	$BA9-87+(-6-543)*-2*1$
19B9	03165	$1+2345+67+8*(-9A+B)$	$B-(A+9-8)+76+5*(432+1)$
19BA	03166	$1+23+4*-56*-7-8-9A*-B$	$-BA9+87+6*(543+21)$
19BB	03167	$-12-(3+45*(-67-8))-9AB$	$-B+A+98-7-6+5*(432-1)$
1A00	03168	$-1+2345+67*-8-9-AB$	$-B+A+9*(8-76-5)*-4-(-32+1)$
1A01	03169	$-12-3*-45-6*7*8*9*(A-B)$	$BA+9*87-(-65-4-3)*21$
1A02	03170	$12+34*(56+7)+89+AB$	$BA9-8*7*(-65+43)+2-1$
1A03	03171	$1234+5+6-78*(9-A-B)$	$B+A+987-65+4*321$
1A04	03172	$-1-2*3-4*-567+(8+9)*(A-B)$	$BA9+8-(76+543*-2+1)$
1A05	03173	$-12+3-45*(-67-8)-9AB$	$-B+A9-8*-7*(-6+54-3)-21$
1A06	03174	$-1+23+45*67+89*-A+B$	$BA9+8-(76-543*2-1)$
1A07	03175	$-12+3*(-4+5)*(678-(-9A+B))$	$BA9+8*-7+6*(-5*-43-2*1)$
1A08	03176	$-1+23+(4+56)*(7-8*9+A)*B$	$BA+9+8*76-5*(-4-321)$
1A09	03177	$-1+2-3+4*(567-(8+9-A))+B$	$-B-(-A98-(76-543*-2*1))$
1A0A	03178	$1234-56-(-7+8+9*-AB)$	$-B-(-A98-76+543*-2-1)$
1A0B	03179	$-1+2345+6*-78-(9+A)*B$	$-B*(-A+98-76-5+4*-3*21)$
1A10	03180	$-1*(234-5-(6+7-8))*(-9+A-B)$	$-B+A9-8+7-6+5*432-1$
1A11	03181	$1234-5*(6-7)+8*(9+AB)$	$B-A-(987-6*543)-21$
1A12	03182	$1234-5*-67-8*-9*A+B$	$B+A+(9-8)*76-5*-432+1$
1A13	03183	$12-3+4-56*(78-9-AB)$	$B+A+9-8+76-(-5*432-1)$
1A14	03184	$-12-3-(4*-567+89+A*-B)$	$-B+A9-8-7+6-5*(-432-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1A15	03185	$1-2+3*(456-7)+89A+B$	$BA9-(-876-5*43+21)$
1A16	03186	$1*(-234+56-78)*9*(A-B)$	$B-(-A+9-87)-(-6+5*(-432+1))$
1A17	03187	$1+23-(-45*-6*-7-8*9A)-B$	$BA-(-9-8)-(-7*6-5*432*1)$
1A18	03188	$-1+2+3-45*(-67-8)-9AB$	$B-A+98+7-6-5*-432*1$
1A19	03189	$1234+5-6-(-789-A-B)$	$-B+A*98-(-76+5)*-4*-3*2*1$
1A1A	03190	$-1-2+3*(-4+5-6+789)-AB$	$BA-9+8*-7*65+4321$
1A1B	03191	$1234-5+6+789+A+B$	$B-(A-98+7-6+5*(-432-1))$
1A20	03192	$12*-3*-4*(-5+6)*(-7-89+AB)$	$-B+A*98-(76-543)*(2+1)$
1A21	03193	$-1+2345-(678+(-9-A)*B)$	$-B+A9+876-(-5+4*-321)$
1A22	03194	$12+3*-4*-5*-67-8*9*-A*B$	$B+A*-98+765*4+3*(2-1)$
1A23	03195	$1+2-3*(4-5-(678-(-9A+B)))$	$-B-A*-9-8*-7-6*-5*-43*2*-1$
1A24	03196	$1+2345+6*78+9A*-B$	$B-A*98+765*4+(-3-2)*-1$
1A25	03197	$1-2-3+4*567-89-A*-B$	$-B-A9+87-65*(-4-32*1)$
1A26	03198	$1+2*3*(456-(78+9+A))+B$	$-B+A+98+7+6-5*-432*1$
1A27	03199	$-1*(23+4*-5)*(6*(7-89)+AB)$	$B+A98+76+543*-2*-1$
1A28	03200	$1-(2+3)-456*-7-(-8-9A*-B)$	$B+A98+76-543*-2+1$
1A29	03201	$1234+5+6+7+8+9A*B$	$BA9+87+654+321$
1A2A	03202	$-12+3*(4-(-5-678-9A)-B)$	$-BA-(9+87)+6*-54*3*(-2-1)$
1A2B	03203	$1+2345-(67*8+9A)+B$	$BA9-8+76+54*(-3+21)$
1A30	03204	$1*-2*(-3+4*-56+78-9AB)$	$BA-9+8*(-7+6)*54*3*-2-1$
1A31	03205	$-12-3-4*-567-89+AB$	$BA9-8-7*6+543*2*1$
1A32	03206	$1234-56-78+9A*B$	$-B+A-(9*-87+6*5*(-43-21))$
1A33	03207	$-1-2-3+456*7-89A-B$	$-B-A+987+6-5+4*321$
1A34	03208	$123-4+5*67*8-(9+A*B)$	$-B+A-9-8-7+65*(4+32)-1$
1A35	03209	$1-23+4*(567+8-(-9A+B))+B$	$-B-A-987-6*-543+2+1$
1A36	03210	$-12+3*-456*(7-8)+9A*B$	$BA9+87-6-(5+43)*-21$
1A37	03211	$12-3-4*-567-8-9+A+B$	$BA9+876-5*-43+2-1$
1A38	03212	$-1+2345-(-6-(7*-89-(A-B)))$	$BA9+8*-7-(-6-543)*2+1$
1A39	03213	$1+2-3+456*7-89A-B$	$BA9-8-76+5*-4*(-32-1)$
1A3A	03214	$1234+56+78-9A*-B$	$B-(-A-9+8+7-(6+5-4)*321)$
1A3B	03215	$1+23+45-6*7*8*-9+A*B$	$-B+A9*(-87-(-65-43))+2-1$
1A40	03216	$1234+5+(-6+78+9+A)*B$	$BA+9-(-876+5+4*321)$
1A41	03217	$-1-(-2-3)-(-456*7+89A+B)$	$B+A9+(-8+76-5+4)*32-1$
1A42	03218	$1*2*(-3-4*56*-7-(89+AB))$	$BA-98*-76+5-4321$
1A43	03219	$1234-(-56+78+9A*-B)$	$BA-987+6*(543-21)$
1A44	03220	$1234+5*6+789-(-A-B)$	$BA9+8-7+6-5*-4*-3*-21$
1A45	03221	$-1-2*-3+4*567+8-9+A+B$	$BA9+8-(-7*-6-543*2*-1)$
1A46	03222	$1+23+4*567-(-8+9-A+B)$	$-BA9+876*5+43*21$
1A47	03223	$1234-56+789+A*B$	$BA-9-(-8-7)+6-(5*-432+1)$
1A48	03224	$1234+56-(-789+A)-B$	$B-A98-7+6*(543+21)$
1A49	03225	$-1+234+5+6*-7*-8*9-AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6*-5*43*-2-1$
1A4A	03226	$-12-3*-4*-5*-6*(-7+8)*9*(-A+B)$	$BA+9-(-876-5-4*321)$
1A4B	03227	$1+2345+6*7*(-8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A-987-(-6*543-2)-1$
1A50	03228	$12+3*456+7+89A+B$	$BA+9+8-7+6+5*-432*-1$
1A51	03229	$-1-2345+(67-8)*(-9+A*B)$	$-BA9-8+76*(5+43-(2-1))$
1A52	03230	$1*2345+6*7-8+9*-A+B$	$-BA-98*-7*6+5*4*-3*21$
1A53	03231	$1234-(-5+67-89A)-B$	$-B+A*9-8+76+5*432*1$
1A54	03232	$-12-3+4-56*-7*(8+9-A)+B$	$B+A+9*8+7+6+5*(4+3-2)+1$
1A55	03233	$-1-2+3+4+5*6*(-7-89)-AB$	$BA9+8-(-7-65)*(-4-3+21)$
1A56	03234	$-12*3*(4-56+78-9A+B)$	$-B*(-A-9-87+65-4)*3*2*1$
1A57	03235	$1-(-2+3+456*-7-(-89A+B))$	$BA9-87+(65+4*-3)*21$
1A58	03236	$-123-4+5-(-67-89)*AB$	$B+A-987+6*(543-2)*1$
1A59	03237	$-1-(-2345+6)-7*8*9+AB$	$BA-(9-(-8-7*-6))-5*-432*-1$
1A5A	03238	$1-(2-3*456)-(-7-8)+9A*B$	$-B+A-98*-7-6-54*-32+1$
1A5B	03239	$12-(-3-4*567-(-89+AB))$	$-BA-(9-87*-6*-5+4*-3*21)$
1A60	03240	$-1*23*-4*(-5+6)*(-78-9+AB)$	$-B-A+98+7*6*54+321$
1A61	03241	$1234+5-67+89A-B$	$B-A-(987+654*(-3-2))-1$
1A62	03242	$12+3+(45+6)*-7*-8-9*A+B$	$B+A9-87*-6*5+4*-3*(-2+1)$
1A63	03243	$12+34*-56*-7-89AB$	$-B+A98+765-(-432+1)$
1A64	03244	$1234-56-(-789-AB)$	$-B+A98+765+432*1$
1A65	03245	$-1*(-2+3)*(456+7)*(89-A*B)$	$-B+A98+765+432+1$
1A66	03246	$123-456*-7-(-8+9AB)$	$-B-(A98-7-6+54*3*-21)$
1A67	03247	$-12-3*-456-78+9AB$	$-B+A+987-(-654+3)*2-1$
1A68	03248	$-12*(3-(4-(-5-6)))-(-78-9+AB))$	$BA9-8+7-6+543*2*1$
1A69	03249	$-123*(-4-(-5-67))-(-8+9A-B))$	$-B+A*98-(-76+5+4-3)*21$
1A6A	03250	$1+23-4*-567-89+AB$	$B+A-987+6*543+2*1$
1A6B	03251	$1234-(-5+6)-(-78+9A*-B)$	$BA9-8+765+4+321$
1A70	03252	$1234-56-7+89A-B$	$B-(A98-765*4)+321$
1A71	03253	$1234-5-(67-89A)+B$	$-BA-(987+6)-54*3*-21$
1A72	03254	$-12-3+4*(567-8)-(-9A+B)$	$BA9+8+7*(-65+4)*-3*(2-1)$
1A73	03255	$-1-23+4+5*-67*-8+9+A*B$	$BA+98+(-76+5+4)*(-32+1)$
1A74	03256	$1-2-(-3-45*67-8*-9A-B)$	$B*(A9-(-87-6-54+3+2+1))$
1A75	03257	$-1-2-3-4-5*6*7*-8+9+AB$	$B+A-9*8*7+6*5*4-3*2-1$
1A76	03258	$1-(23+456*-7)-(-8+9A)*B$	$BA9+8*-76-5*(4-321)$
1A77	03259	$1-2-3+4*(567+8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8+765-4+321$
1A78	03260	$1-2-(-3*456+78-9AB)$	$BA9+876+5+4*-3*21$
1A79	03261	$1234+5-(-6-7-8)-9*-AB$	$-B+A9*8-(7+65-4)*(-3-21)$
1A7A	03262	$-12+34*(5+67)-89+A+B$	$BA9+8-7+6+543*-2*-1$
1A7B	03263	$1234+5-67+89A+B$	$B+A9*-8+7*6*(54+32)*1$
1A80	03264	$1*2*(-3-(4-5))*(678-(-9-AB))$	$B-(-A9+87*6*-5+(-4+32))*-1$
1A81	03265	$1234+5*-6*7-8+9AB$	$B+A98-(-765-432)-1$
1A82	03266	$1234+56+789+A+B$	$B-(-A98-765)-432*-1$
1A83	03267	$1-2+34*5+(-6-7)*(-89-AB)$	$B+A98+765+432+1$
1A84	03268	$1234-5-6*7-(-89A+B)$	$B+A+987-65*4*-3*2*1$
1A85	03269	$-1-(-2-34*(-5+67+8)-9)-(A+B)$	$B+A98-(76+54*(-3-21))$
1A86	03270	$-1-2-345*(-6+7-8)+9-AB$	$-B-A98-7*(-65+432*-1)$
1A87	03271	$1234-(-56-78-9*AB)$	$-B+A*-9*(8+7)+6*(543+2-1)$
1A88	03272	$1+23+4*(-5+678-9-AB)$	$BA+9*-87*-6-54*-32*-1$
1A89	03273	$-1*(234-5*678+9*AB)$	$BA9-8*(7+6)*5*(4+3*-2-1)$
1A8A	03274	$1234-56-7+89A+B$	$-B-A*9+(-87-6+54)*-3*21$
1A8B	03275	$12+3*456-78+9AB$	$-B+A-(-98-76-5*-432*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1A90	03276	$1 - (23 - 4 \cdot 567) - (-89 + A) + B$	$B - A + 98 - (-76 - 5 \cdot 432 + 1)$
1A91	03277	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 + 5 \wedge (6 + 7 - 8) - 9 + A - B$	$B + A9 - 8 - 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 + 4321$
1A92	03278	$1234 + 5 - 6 + 789 - A \cdot B$	$B \cdot (A9 + 8 + 76 - (5 - 43 - 21))$
1A93	03279	$1 - 2 - 3 + (-4 + 56) \cdot 7 \cdot 8 + 9 \cdot (-A - B)$	$B + A9 + 87 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 + 43 - 2 \cdot 1$
1A94	03280	$12 - (3 - 4 \cdot 567) + 8 \cdot 9 - (A - B)$	$BA - 98 - 765 \cdot (-4 + 3 - 2) - 1$
1A95	03281	$-1 + 2 \cdot 3 + (-45 + 67) \cdot (89 + A + B)$	$B - A \cdot 9 \cdot 8 - (-76 + 54 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1$
1A96	03282	$1 - (2 + 345 \cdot 6 + 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9) - AB$	$B + A9 - 8 - 7 - 65 \cdot (-4 - 32 + 1)$
1A97	03283	$-12 - 3 - 4 \cdot 567 + 89 + A - B$	$-B - A + 987 + 65 - 4 \cdot 321$
1A98	03284	$1234 + 5 - 6 \cdot 7 + (-89 - A) \cdot B$	$B + A98 - (7 \cdot 6 - (54 + 3) \cdot 21)$
1A99	03285	$-12 - (-3 + 4 + 5 \cdot 67 \cdot 8 - 9 - AB)$	$-B - (-A9 - 87) - (6 + 5 \cdot 432 \cdot 1)$
1A9A	03286	$-1 \cdot (-2 - 34 - (-5 - 6)) \cdot (7 - 8 + 9A - B)$	$-B + A9 + 8 + 76 - 5 \cdot 432 \cdot 1$
1A9B	03287	$-1 \cdot (-2 + 3 - 4 \cdot 5) \cdot (6 \cdot 7 + (8 - 9) \cdot (-AB))$	$-BA + 9 \cdot 87 + 6 - 54 \cdot (-32 - 1)$
1AA0	03288	$-12 - (3 - 4 \cdot 567 - (8 - 9 \cdot A + B))$	$-B - (-A98 + 76 - 54 \cdot 321)$
1AA1	03289	$1234 - 5 - (6 - (789 + AB))$	$-B \cdot (-A9 - 87 - 65 - (-4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
1AA2	03290	$-1 - (-2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \cdot 67 \cdot 8 + 9 - AB)$	$BA + 9 + 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 - 4 - 321$
1AA3	03291	$-1 + 2 \cdot 3 + 45 \cdot (67 - (8 + 9)) \cdot (-A + B)$	$B - (A + 9 \cdot 8 - 7 + 654 \cdot 3) + 2 \cdot 1$
1AA4	03292	$1 - 2 - 3 + (45 + 6) \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9 - (A - B)$	$BA - (-987 + 65 - 4 \cdot 321)$
1AA5	03293	$-1 + 23 + 4 \cdot 567 - 8 + 9AB$	$B - A98 - 7 \cdot (65 - 432) + 1$
1AA6	03294	$-1 \cdot 23 \cdot (45 + 67 - 8 - 9 - AB)$	$-BA9 - 8 + 76 \cdot (5 + 43) - 21$
1AA7	03295	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 + 5 \wedge (6 + 7 - 8) + 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 76 \cdot (-5 + 4 - (32 - 1))$
1AA8	03296	$-12 - 3 - 45 \cdot (-67 - 8) - 9A \cdot B$	$B - A \cdot 98 + (-7 - 65 - 4 + 3) \cdot 2 - 1$
1AA9	03297	$1234 - 5 - 6 - (7 - 89A + B)$	$B - A - 9 + 8 - 7 \cdot (-654 + 321)$
1AAA	03298	$1 + 2345 + 67 \cdot 8 - (-9 + A + B)$	$B - A9 + 8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 \cdot (3 + 21)$
1AAB	03299	$1234 - 56 - (7 - 8) + 9A \cdot B$	$BA + 98 - (-7 - 65 + 4) \cdot 32 + 1$
1AB0	03300	$1234 + 5 + 6 \cdot 7 + 89A + B$	$-B \cdot (-A + 9) \cdot (876 + 543 \cdot 2) \cdot 1$
1AB1	03301	$1234 - 5 - (-6 - 789) + AB$	$BA - (9 - 8 - 76 + 5 \cdot 432 \cdot 1)$
1AB2	03302	$123 + 45 \cdot (-6 + 78) - 9AB$	$B + A + 98 + 76 + 5 \cdot (432 + 1)$
1AB3	03303	$-1/2 + 3 \wedge (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B + A + 987 + 65 - 4 \cdot 321$
1AB4	03304	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5 - 6 - 7) \cdot (89 + AB)$	$BA - (-9 - 8) - (-7 \cdot 6 \cdot 54 - 321)$
1AB5	03305	$-12 - 3 + 4 \cdot 567 - (-89 - A) + B$	$B - A + 987 + 65 - 4 \cdot 321$
1AB6	03306	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot (4 + 567 + 8 \cdot 9 - (-A - B))$	$BA - 9 - 8 \cdot 7 \cdot (-6 + 54) + 3 \cdot 2 - 1$
1AB7	03307	$12 + 3 \cdot (-45 - 6 + 789) + AB$	$B + A9 + 8 + 76 - 5 \cdot 432 - 1$
1AB8	03308	$-1 - 2 + (-3 + 4 \cdot 5) \cdot 6 \cdot (7 + 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B - (-A9 - 87 + 6) - (5 \cdot 432 - 1)$
1AB9	03309	$-1 + 2345 - 6 - 7 \cdot 89 - A \cdot B$	$BA98 + 76 \cdot 54 \cdot 3 + 21$
1ABA	03310	$1234 - 5 \cdot (-6 + 7) + 89A - B$	$B + A98 - 76 + 5 - 4 \cdot 321$
1ABB	03311	$1234 + 5 + 6 + 789 + AB$	$BA9 + 8 + 76 - 5 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 - 1$
1B00	03312	$1234 + 56 - 7 + 89 \cdot A + B$	$BA + 98 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54 + 321)$
1B01	03313	$-1 + 2345 - 6 \cdot (78 + 9) - (A + B)$	$-B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 \cdot (-654 + 321)$
1B02	03314	$12 - 3 \cdot (-45 + 67 - 8 - 9A) \cdot B$	$BA + 9 + 87 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 - 1$
1B03	03315	$1 - (2 - 3 \cdot 456) - (-78 + 9A \cdot B)$	$-BA + 9 + 8 \cdot (-76 + 54 + 321)$
1B04	03316	$1234 - 5 - (6 - 78) + 9 \cdot A + B$	$B + A9 + 8 \cdot (76 \cdot 5 - (43 - 2 \cdot 1))$
1B05	03317	$-1 - (2 - 3) - (-4 \cdot 567 - (-8 + 9A) - B)$	$BA9 + 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 - 43 - 21$
1B06	03318	$-1 + 2345 + 67 \cdot 8 - (-9 + A) + B$	$B - A - (9 + 87) \cdot 6 \cdot 5 - (4 + 32 + 1)$
1B07	03319	$1234 - 5 - 6 - 7 - (-89A - B)$	$BA + 9 + 87 - 6 + 5 \cdot 432 + 1$
1B08	03320	$1 - (-2345 - 67 \cdot 8 - 9) - (A - B)$	$B - (-A9 - 87 - 6 + 5 \cdot 432) + 1$
1B09	03321	$1234 - (-5 + 6 - 7) - (-89A + B)$	$B + A \cdot (-9 - 8 - (-76 + 5 \cdot 43) + 2 + 1)$
1B0A	03322	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (-3 - 4 + 5 \cdot 67 - 89A + B)$	$-BA - 9 - 8 \cdot (7 - 6 \cdot 54) + 321$
1B0B	03323	$1234 - (5 - (6 + 7)) - (-89A + B)$	$-BA + 9 \cdot (8 - 7 - 65 + 4 + 321)$
1B10	03324	$1234 - 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 - 8) - 9A \cdot B$	$BA + 98 + 7 - 6 + 5 \cdot (432 - 1)$
1B11	03325	$1234 + 5 - (-6 + 7) - (89 + A) \cdot B$	$BA + 9 + 87 + 6 - 5 \cdot (-432 + 1)$
1B12	03326	$-1 + 23 + 4 \cdot (567 - 89 + AB)$	$-BA + 9 \cdot 87 - 65 \cdot (4 - 32 + 1)$
1B13	03327	$-1 - 2 - (3 + 4 \cdot 567 - 8) - (-9A - B)$	$BA - (-98 + 7) - (-6 - 5 \cdot 432 \cdot 1)$
1B14	03328	$12 - 3 - (4 \cdot 567 + 8 - 9A) + B$	$BA - (-98 - 7) - 6 - (5 \cdot 432 + 1)$
1B15	03329	$1234 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89A + B$	$B - A9 - 8 \cdot 76 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 32 - 1$
1B16	03330	$1 + 2 - 3 \cdot (4 + 56 \cdot (7 + 8) + 9) \cdot AB$	$BA + 98 + 7 - 6 + 5 \cdot 432 + 1$
1B17	03331	$1234 - 5 + 6 - 7 - (-89A - B)$	$BA + 9 + 87 + 6 - 5 \cdot 432 + 1$
1B18	03332	$-1 + 2 + (-345 - 6) \cdot 7 - 89 + A - B$	$-BA - 9 \cdot 8 + 7 \cdot 6 \cdot (-5 - 43 - 21)$
1B19	03333	$1234 - 5 - (6 - 7 - 89A) + B$	$-B \cdot (A9 + 8 - 76 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 3 - 2) \cdot 1$
1B1A	03334	$-1234 + 5 \cdot (678 - 9 + AB)$	$BA + 98 - (-7 + 6) - 5 \cdot (-432 - 1)$
1B1B	03335	$1234 - 56 - 78 + 9AB$	$BA9 - (-876 + 5 \cdot (-43 - 21))$
1B20	03336	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot (7 + 8 - (9 + AB))$	$BA9 - (8 - 76 + 543 \cdot 2) - 1$
1B21	03337	$1 \cdot (-2 - (34 + 5)) \cdot (-6 + 7 + 8 \cdot 9) \cdot (-A + B)$	$-BA9 - (8 - 76 - 543 \cdot 2 \cdot 1)$
1B22	03338	$1234 + 5 + 6 + 78 - 9 \cdot AB$	$-B + A98 + 7 - 6 + 54 \cdot (3 + 21)$
1B23	03339	$-1 - 2 + 3 \cdot 4 + (-5 \cdot 6 + 7 \cdot 8) \cdot (-9A - B)$	$BA + 987 - 6 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 321$
1B24	03340	$-123 + 4 - 56 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9 \cdot (A + B)$	$BA + 98 + 7 + 6 - 5 \cdot 432 - 1$
1B25	03341	$1234 + 5 + 6 - (7 - 89A - B)$	$BA - 9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4 - 32 - 1)$
1B26	03342	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (-345 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 \cdot A - B)$	$BA + 98 + 7 - (-6 + 5 \cdot 432 - 1)$
1B27	03343	$1234 + 5 - 6 - (-7 - 89A) + B$	$BA + 9 + 87 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 + 43 \cdot 2 \cdot 1$
1B28	03344	$1 + 2 - 34 \cdot (-56 - 7 - 8) - 9 - A \cdot B$	$BA - 987 - 6 \cdot 543 - 21$
1B29	03345	$1234 - (5 - 6) - (-7 - 89A - B)$	$-B - (A + 9) - (-8 - 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 \cdot (3 + 21))$
1B2A	03346	$-1 - 23 + 456 \cdot 7 + 8 \cdot (-9 - AB)$	$B + A + 9 - 8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5 + 4) \cdot 3 - 2 - 1$
1B2B	03347	$-1 - 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 - 56 - 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot (-A + B)$	$BA9 + 87 - 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 43 - 2 - 1$
1B30	03348	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (56 + 7 - 89 - A + B)$	$BA + 9 - 87 - (-6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 1$
1B31	03349	$1234 + 56 + 7 - (8 - 9A) \cdot B$	$BA - 9 + 8 \cdot 76 - 54 \cdot (-32 - 1)$
1B32	03350	$-1 - 2 - 3 \cdot 456 \cdot (-7 + 8) + 9AB$	$B + A9 - 8 - (765 - 4) \cdot 3 - 2 - 1$
1B33	03351	$-1 + 23 \cdot 45 \cdot (-6 - 7) - 89AB$	$BA9 + 87 - 6 + 543 \cdot 2 - 1$
1B34	03352	$1234 + 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 - 9A \cdot B$	$BA9 + 87 - 6 + 543 \cdot 2 \cdot 1$
1B35	03353	$1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 5 \cdot 678 - 9AB$	$BA9 - (-8 - 76 + 543 \cdot 2 \cdot 1)$
1B36	03354	$12 + 34 - 5 \cdot 67 \cdot 8 + 9 + AB$	$B - A9 + 8 \cdot 7 \cdot (6 - (-5 - 432)) \cdot 1$
1B37	03355	$1234 - (-5 - 6) - (-7 - 89A) + B$	$BA - 9 \cdot (87 - (-6 + 5 + 4 + 321))$
1B38	03356	$-1 - (-234 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (-78 - 9)) - (-A + B)$	$BA - 987 - 6 \cdot (-543 + 2) - 1$
1B39	03357	$1 - 23 - 4 \cdot (-5 - 678 + 9A) + B$	$B + A \cdot 9 - 8 \cdot 7 + (65 + 43) \cdot 2 \cdot 1$
1B3A	03358	$1234 - 5 - 6 + 7 - (-8 - 9A \cdot B)$	$-B - (A - 9 \cdot 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 - 1)$
1B3B	03359	$1 + 2 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot (9 - A + B)$	$-B + A \cdot 98 - (76 - 5) \cdot (-43 + 21)$
1B40	03360	$1 + 234 - 5 \cdot 67 \cdot 8 - 9A - B$	$-B + A9 - (8 - (-765 + 4)) \cdot 3 - 2 - 1$
1B41	03361	$1 + 23 - 4 \cdot 567 + 8 + 9A + B$	$BA9 - 87 - 65 + 4 \cdot 321$
1B42	03362	$-12 + 34 \cdot 56 + 7 \cdot 89 - A + B$	$-B - (A - 9 + 8) - (-76 - (-5 + 4)) \cdot 32 \cdot 1$
1B43	03363	$1 + 23 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 + 7 - (-8 - 9A + B)$	$B - A + 98 \cdot (76 - 54 + 3) + 2 \cdot 1$
1B44	03364	$1234 + 5 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 9A \cdot B$	$-BA - (-9 + 8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot 5 + 43 \cdot 2 + 1)$
1B45	03365	$1 + 23 + 4 \cdot 567 + 8 \cdot (9 + A) - B$	$BA9 + 87 - (-6 + 543 \cdot 2 - 1)$
1B46	03366	$-12 + 3 - (-4 \cdot 567 + 8 + 9) \cdot (-A - B)$	$-B \cdot (A9 + 87 - (65 + 4 + 321))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
1B47	03367	$12+3-4*(-567-8)-9+AB$	$-B-A9+876+5*(-4+321)$
1B48	03368	$-12-3*(-456-7)+8+9AB$	$BA-987-6*543-2+1$
1B49	03369	$123+4*(567+8)-9-(A+B)$	$-B+A98-(-7+6)-5+4*321$
1B4A	03370	$1234-5-(-6-(7+8)-9A*B)$	$-B-A-9*-87+65*(4+3+21)$
1B4B	03371	$1234-56+7*-8+9AB$	$BA-987+6*543-2*-1$
1B50	03372	$1-23*-456+7-89A*B$	$-B+A9*-8+765*4+3*21$
1B51	03373	$-12+345*(6-(7-8))-9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9*8+(7+6+543)*(2+1)$
1B52	03374	$12+3+4-(-5*678+9AB)$	$B+A*98*7+65*(-4+32-1)$
1B53	03375	$-1*-23*(-45+67-8+9A-B)$	$BA-(987+6*(-543-(2-1)))$
1B54	03376	$1234+56+789+AB$	$B-A-9+(-8+765+43)*(2+1)$
1B55	03377	$1+2-(-3+4+(-5-6*7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B-(-A98-(-7-6))-(-5-4*321)$
1B56	03378	$1-23*-45+678+9*-A*-B$	$-B+A9*(8+76)-(5432-1)$
1B57	03379	$1234-(56+7-(-8-9A))*-B$	$-B+A*-9-87*(6*5-4)+3-21$
1B58	03380	$1234-5-6-78+9AB$	$BA+9+87-6*(-54-321)$
1B59	03381	$1+23-45-(-67+89)*-AB$	$B+A98-(-7*65+43*-21)$
1B5A	03382	$12-3*-456+7+8+9AB$	$-B-A+9-8-7*(-65-4)*3*2*1$
1B5B	03383	$1+2-34*(5+6-78)-(-9-AB)$	$-BA-(98+7+6*(5-432+1))$
1B60	03384	$1-2-3+4*(-5-6-7+89-A)*B$	$BA+9*8*(-7+6-5+43)+2*1$
1B61	03385	$1-2+34*(5+67)-(89-AB)$	$B-A+9*8*(7+6-5+4+3+2-1)$
1B62	03386	$-12-(-3-(-4-5))-(-67-89)*AB$	$B+A+9*87+6+54*-32*-1$
1B63	03387	$-1+2+3-4*(-5-(678-9A))+B$	$B-(-A98+7)-6-(-5-4*321)$
1B64	03388	$1*-2*(-34+5+67-8+9A)*-B$	$-B+A+9-8+(76+54)*(-3+21)$
1B65	03389	$1234-(5-67)-(-89A+B)$	$BA+987-65*(4-3-21)$
1B66	03390	$-1-2+34+5*678-9AB$	$BA+98*(7-(-6+5+4))*(3*2+1)$
1B67	03391	$1234-5-67-8+9AB$	$BA+9*(8-7-(65+4-321))$
1B68	03392	$1234-(5-6+78-9AB)$	$BA9+876-5*4+321$
1B69	03393	$1234-(-5-6*7)-(-8+9A*-B)$	$BA-9+87-65*(-4-32+1)$
1B6A	03394	$-1+2345-(67-89)*(A-B)$	$-BA+98+76*(-5+4)*32*-1$
1B6B	03395	$1*(-2-3)*(-456+78-(9A+B))$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5+4)^3-2+1$
1B70	03396	$1234-5*-6+(7-8-9)*-AB$	$-B-(-A+9+8*7*6-5*432*1)$
1B71	03397	$-12+34*(5-6+78-9)+AB$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5+4)^3+2-1$
1B72	03398	$1234+56+7+89A-B$	$B+A-987-6*(-543-21)$
1B73	03399	$1234-(-5-67-89A)-B$	$B*(A9-(-87-65))*(4-(-3-2*1))$
1B74	03400	$123+456*7+(-89-A)*B$	$-B+A98+7+65*-4*-3*2*1$
1B75	03401	$1234+5-(67+8-9AB)$	$B-A+9*8-(7+6)*(-5*43-2+1)$
1B76	03402	$1234+5+6-78+9AB$	$B+A98-(7-65*4*3)*2+1$
1B77	03403	$1234+56+78+9*AB$	$BA9-8+765+432-1$
1B78	03404	$-1234-5*(67+8+9*-AB)$	$BA9-8+765+432*1$
1B79	03405	$1234+5-6*7+(-8-9A)*-B$	$BA9-8+765-(-432-1)$
1B7A	03406	$1234+56-7+89A+B$	$-B-(-A+987)-(-6-54*-3*-21)$
1B7B	03407	$1234-5-67+8+9AB$	$BA9-8-7*(-65-4)*3+2-1$
1B80	03408	$1+2-(345*(-6+7-8)-9A-B)$	$BA*(9+8)*(7+6-5-(4+3+21))$
1B81	03409	$-12-3+456*7+8*9*-A*-B$	$B+A98-7-65*-4*-3*2+1$
1B82	03410	$-1+2+3*456+7*8+9AB$	$B*A*(-98+76+5*4*(-32+1))$
1B83	03411	$-1+2*3*45*6+7*8*(-9A)*B$	$BA9+876-5+4+321$
1B84	03412	$1234-56-7-8+9AB$	$-B+A*98-7*6-5*(-4-321)$
1B85	03413	$12-(-345+6*7*8*9)+A*-B$	$BA9+876+5+4+321$
1B86	03414	$-123-4-5*(6-7)*-8*-9*A-B$	$-BA+9-(-876+5*(-4-321))$
1B87	03415	$1234+56-7-8+9A*B$	$B+A-9+8*7/6*(5+4)^3/2+1$
1B88	03416	$-12*(3-(45+67+8))-(-9A-B)$	$B+A-9*8-7-6+(5-4^3)^2-1$
1B89	03417	$1234+5-(67-8-9AB)$	$BA+98+76-5*-432-1$
1B8A	03418	$1*2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9A-B$	$-BA-98*-7-6*(-5+4-321)$
1B8B	03419	$-1+2345-6*(-7-8*-9)-AB$	$BA9+8+765+432-1$
1B90	03420	$123*4*-5*(-6-7*(8-9))*(A-B)$	$-BA9-876+5*-43*-21$
1B91	03421	$1234+5+67-(-89A-B)$	$BA9-(-8-765)-(-432-1)$
1B92	03422	$1-2-3+456*7-8*9*A*-B$	$BA+98-7*(6-(5-4+321))$
1B93	03423	$1*2-3+4+5*6*(-7-(8-9A)+B)$	$B+A98+7+65*4*-3*-2+1$
1B94	03424	$-1-23*4*5*-6+7*8+9A+B$	$-BA+9-87-6*(5-432-1)$
1B95	03425	$-1-2345-(-6-7*-89*-A)+B$	$B-A+987*-6*-5-4+321$
1B96	03426	$1234-(56-7)-(8-9AB)$	$-BA9*(-8-7+6+5+4-3+2-1)$
1B97	03427	$1+23-4*-567-8*-9+AB$	$BA9-87-6-5+4*321$
1B98	03428	$1234-56-(7-8-9AB)$	$-B+A-9*-87+6+54*(32+1)$
1B99	03429	$1234+56-(-7-(-8-9A*-B))$	$B+A9-8-7*(-654+321)$
1B9A	03430	$-1-(-2+3+4*-567-89)+AB$	$BA9-8-76*-5-43*-21$
1B9B	03431	$-12-3*-456+78+9AB$	$BA9-8+7*(65+4)*3+21$
1BA0	03432	$-1*(-2+3)*(-45+67)*(8-9-AB)$	$BA9+876+5*4+321$
1BA1	03433	$-1-2*-34+(-56+78)*(9A+B)$	$BA-9-(87-654)*(3+2-1)$
1BA2	03434	$-1234-5*(-6-(7-8))*(9-AB)$	$-B-A+9*8*-76*-5-43+21$
1BA3	03435	$-1-2*3*4+5*-6*7*(-8-9)-A*B$	$B+A9+87*(6-(-54+32))-1$
1BA4	03436	$-1+2-(-3-4*567-89)+AB$	$-BA-9*-87*-6+5*-4*-321$
1BA5	03437	$12-3*-4+5-(-67+89)*-AB$	$BA9-(87+6-5+4*-321)$
1BA6	03438	$123+4*567-8*-9-(-A+B)$	$B-A+9+8*7*(654-321)$
1BA7	03439	$1+23+4*567+89+A*B$	$B-A9-87+6*(-5+432+1)$
1BA8	03440	$1*(2+3)*(4+567-8-(9A-B))$	$B-A9-(876+54*3*-21)$
1BA9	03441	$1-2-34-(5*-678+9A*B)$	$BA-(-9+8*-7-65*(4+32*1))$
1BAA	03442	$123+4*(567-8)+9A-B$	$B+A+9-8-76*(5-4)*-32*1$
1BAB	03443	$1+2345+6-(-7*8*-9-A+B)$	$-B+A98-7+65*-4*-321$
1BB0	03444	$123+4*567-(-8-(9A))*B$	$B+A9-8-(-7-6)*-5*43-(-2+1)$
1BB1	03445	$1234-(-5+6-78)-9A*-B$	$B+A9+8-7*(-654+321)$
1BB2	03446	$12+3*-4*(-5+6)*(78-9A)*B$	$BA+987-(-65+4*-321)$
1BB3	03447	$1234-5-(-6-78)+9A*B$	$-BA-(98+7)+654*(3+2-1)$
1BB4	03448	$1234-(-5+6)+7-(-8-9A)*B$	$B-A-9-8*-76*5+4-32*1$
1BB5	03449	$123-(4-5*67*8+9-AB)$	$BA9-8-7-(65+4*-321)$
1BB6	03450	$1-2+34*(5+67-(-8+9))+AB$	$-B-A*9+8*-76*-5-43-2*-1$
1BB7	03451	$1+2+3-45*(6+7)*(89-A*B)$	$-B+A9*8-76*(5-4-3-21)$
1BB8	03452	$-1+23-4*-5-(-67+89)*-AB$	$-BA-9+8+(-7+65)*43+21$
1BB9	03453	$1234+5-6*(-78-(9+AB))$	$-B+A-98+(-76+5)*(4+32)*-1$
1BBA	03454	$1234+5*-6-(-7-(8+9AB))$	$BA-9*8*(7-(6+5+4)-32)*1$
1BBB	03455	$(1+2+3)^4*5-6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA-9+87*(-6-5+4)*(-3-2)+1$
2000	03456	$1*-23*4*(-5+6-7+89-AB)$	$B-A+9+8*76*5-43+21$
2001	03457	$1234-5-(6+7)-(8-9AB)$	$BA9+8*(7-6+54*3+21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2002	03458	$123+45-6*7*(8+9-A)*-B$	$-B+A98-(-76+5)+4*321$
2003	03459	$-1234-5+6*7*8*(9-A+B)$	$-B+A*(-98+7)*-6-5*432*1$
2004	03460	$1+23-4*-567+89+AB$	$B+A-9+8*(-76+54+321)$
2005	03461	$-12+3*-4*-5*6*7+8*9A+B$	$-BA9+87+(-6-5)*(-4-321)$
2006	03462	$1*-2*(3-456-789+A+B)$	$BA+987-6*54*(-3-2)+1$
2007	03463	$-123-45*(-67+8)-9A-B$	$BA9+87*-6-54*(-32+1)$
2008	03464	$-1*-2*(3+456-78-9*-AB)$	$BA9+8-76+5-4*-321$
2009	03465	$-1*(2-34-(-56-7))*(-8-9A+B)$	$BA9+876-5*43*2*-1$
200A	03466	$-1-(2-34*56)-(-78*-9A)+B$	$BA9+876-5*-43*2+1$
200B	03467	$1234+56-78+9AB$	$BA9-(8-76*-5*-4)-32*1$
2010	03468	$1*(23-(4-(5+6)))*(-78-(-9A-B))$	$BA9-87+6*5-4*-321$
2011	03469	$-1+2345-(-678+9AB)$	$B+A-9+8-7+6*54*-3*(-2-1)$
2012	03470	$1*2345-(-678+9AB)$	$-B+A98+(-7-(-65-4)+3)*21$
2013	03471	$1+2345+678-9AB$	$-B-(A9+8*76*-5-4)+3*2+1$
2014	03472	$1234-(5+6)-(-7+8)*-9AB$	$BA9-87-(654+3)*2*-1$
2015	03473	$1-2*(-3-(-45-6))*(-7-8-(9-(-A-B)))$	$BA9-(8+7*6+5*43)-21$
2016	03474	$-1-234-56*7*8-(-9A+B)$	$-BA+98-(-7+65)*(-43-(-2+1))$
2017	03475	$-12-(-3-4+5*-678)+9A*-B$	$-B-(A+98+7*6*(-54+3-21))$
2018	03476	$1+2*3+4*5*(67+89-A)-B$	$BA9+876+54+321$
2019	03477	$123-4*-567+(-8-9)*-A*B$	$B+A9-(-8+76*(5-4-32)+1)$
201A	03478	$-1-2+3-4-5*-678+9A*-B$	$-B-A-9+8*7*-6*-5+4*321$
201B	03479	$1234+5-(-6+7)-8+9AB$	$B+A98+7+65+4*321$
2020	03480	$1*(2+3)*(-4+567+8-(9A-B))$	$-B-(-A-9*8*7*6)-(-5+4)*321$
2021	03481	$1234-(-5+6-7+8)+9AB$	$B+A+9^A(-8+7)*6^A5^A4+3+2-1$
2022	03482	$1-2*(-3*-4-5^6-7*8)/9+A-B$	$-B+A98-(7+6-54)*32-1$
2023	03483	$1234-5+6+7-8+9AB$	$-B-A*9*8+7*(-6-5+432-1)$
2024	03484	$-1+2+3*(45-6+789-(A-B))$	$BA+98-7-65*(-4-32)-1$
2025	03485	$1234-5+6-7+8+9AB$	$BA9+8-7*-6*(5-4*-3+21)$
2026	03486	$-1*2*(-345-(6-7+89A-B))$	$-B-A9-8*-76*5+4-3+21$
2027	03487	$1234-(5-(-6+7)-8-9A-B)$	$-B*(A9-876-(-543-21))$
2028	03488	$-1-23+45*6*7-8-9A*-B$	$BA+98-(76+5)*(-4+32)*-1$
2029	03489	$-1-(234-56*7*8)-(9-AB)$	$BA+9+8-76*(-5-4-3-21)$
202A	03490	$-1+2*3-4*(-567-89)-AB$	$-B-A+9+(-8-76-5)*(-4+32)*-1$
202B	03491	$1-23*-45-67*-8+9AB$	$-BA-9*87+6*5*4*-32*-1$
2030	03492	$1-23-456*7+8*(9-AB)$	$B-A9-(87+6*(-5-432))+1$
2031	03493	$-123+4*(-56+789-AB)$	$B-(-A9+87)-6*54*-3*(2+1)$
2032	03494	$123+456*7-(-8+9*AB)$	$-B-A*-9+8*-7*(6-54-3)-2+1$
2033	03495	$-1-(-2-3*4)-(-5*678+9A*B)$	$-B-A-(-9*8-(7+65))^A(4+32-1)$
2034	03496	$1234+5*6*(-78+9+AB)$	$BA9-(8+7-6*-5+4*-321)$
2035	03497	$1+234-56*(78-9-AB)$	$BA9+87+6+(-54-3)*-21$
2036	03498	$-1*(-2-(-34+5))*(-6+7)*(-89-(-A+B))$	$B-A98-76*(-5-43)+2+1$
2037	03499	$1234-5+6+7+8+9AB$	$-B+A*(98+7)-6*5*(-43-21)$
2038	03500	$12*(34+5+6-(-78-9A)-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7+6^A5^A4/3^A2-1$
2039	03501	$(-1-2+3-4-5*-6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-BA-98+7*(-65+432)*1$
203A	03502	$12+3-4*(-567-89)-AB$	$-BA+98+(7+65)*A(4+32)*1$
203B	03503	$-12-3-4*(5+6)*(-78-9A+B)$	$-BA-9*(-8-7+6*54-(3-(-2-1)))$
2040	03504	$123-4*-567+8+9A+B$	$B+A+9*(8-7+65+43)*A(2+1)$
2041	03505	$-1+2*3*4*(5-6)*-78-9A*-B$	$BA9-8*7*(6-5+4-(32-1))$
2042	03506	$1*2*(345-6-7+89A+B)$	$BA-9*-87-(-6-54*32+1)$
2043	03507	$1+2-(3-(45*-6*-7+89A+B))$	$B-A*-98*7-(6*543-2*1)$
2044	03508	$-1-2-34*-56-7*(-8-9A)-B$	$B-A9-(-8*-76*-5-43+21)$
2045	03509	$1234+5-(-6-(7+8))+9AB$	$B*(A+9-(8-7)+6-5+4*3^21)$
2046	03510	$-1*2*(34+5)*6-(7+8+9A+B))$	$BA9-8+76*5*4-(-3-2)*1$
2047	03511	$-1-234+5*-6*(-7+8-9A-B)$	$-B+A98*7-6+5-4321$
2048	03512	$1234-5-6*-7-8+9AB$	$BA9+8-7*6+5-4*-321$
2049	03513	$1+23-45*-6*7+89A-B$	$-B-A98*-7+6-5-4321$
204A	03514	$1*2*(3+456+789+A-B)$	$BA9+8+7*(65+43)*2+1$
204B	03515	$1-(2+345+6*-7*(89-A))+B$	$BA9-87+65+4*321$
2050	03516	$-1*2*(3+456+789)*(-A-B)$	$B-A9+8*76*5-4-32*-1$
2051	03517	$-12+34-(-5*6*(7+89)-AB)$	$-B-A9*-8*(7-6)+54*(32+1)$
2052	03518	$1234+5*6*78-9A*B$	$BA9+8*7+(-654-3)*-2-1$
2053	03519	$1234+5-6*(-7-89-AB)$	$BA-987+6*(543+21)$
2054	03520	$123-4-5*-678-9AB$	$B*-A*(9-(8+76)+54-3*2-1)$
2055	03521	$-1-2-345*-6-7*8*-9A*B$	$BA9+8+76*-5*-4*(-3+2)*-1$
2056	03522	$-1234+56*(78-9)+A*B$	$-BA+98*-7+6*(543-21)$
2057	03523	$12+345+6*7*8*-9*(-A+B)$	$-BA-9+876-54*32*-1$
2058	03524	$-1*(-234+567*(8+9-(A+B)))$	$-B+A9-8*-7*6-5*432*-1$
2059	03525	$1+2-(-34-5*678-9A*-B)$	$BA9-8-7-6+5+4*321$
205A	03526	$1234+5-(-67-(-8-9A)*-B)$	$BA9+87*-6+54*32-1$
205B	03527	$12-3-45*6*-7-8-9A*-B$	$BA9+8-(76*-5*4-3*-2*-1)$
2060	03528	$12*(3+4+5)*(-6-78+9A*B)$	$-B-A-9-876-54*3*3-21$
2061	03529	$1-2*(-345+67*8)*(9-A-B)$	$BA9-8-(-7+6)-(-5-4*321)$
2062	03530	$1+2345-(6*78-9-AB)$	$-BA+9*(-8+76)*5-(-4-3+21)$
2063	03531	$1*(-2+3*(4-56)-(-7+8+9A))*-B$	$BA9-87+6*54*(3+2)+1$
2064	03532	$1+2-3-45*-6*7+8+9A*B$	$-B+A-9*8-7*(6-54-321)$
2065	03533	$-1+23-45*6*-7-(-89A-B)$	$-BA-9*-87+6*(5-4+321)$
2066	03534	$-123-4567+8*9AB$	$-B-A+9-8*-76*5-43-(2+1)$
2067	03535	$-1*(-23-(4-56))*(-7-8)*(-9-A*-B)$	$B-A98*-7+6-5-4321$
2068	03536	$1-2-34-56*-7*8-9-A*B$	$BA9-876+5*(432-1)$
2069	03537	$-1-23*45-6*7*8*-9-A+B$	$B+A-(-9-876)-5*(4-321)$
206A	03538	$-12-34*-5*6-(-7+89)*(-A-B)$	$-BA9+8-7-6*5*(4+3)*-21$
206B	03539	$-1234+5*(6+789)*(-A+B)$	$BA9-8+7-6+5+4*321$
2070	03540	$-123-4*(-567-8-9A)+B$	$BA9-876+5*432-1$
2071	03541	$-12+3-4+56*7*8-(9+AB)$	$BA9-8+7+6-(5-4*321)$
2072	03542	$-1+2*3+(45-67+8-9)*-AB$	$BA9-(876-5*432-1)$
2073	03543	$12-3+4*(567+89-A-B)$	$BA9+8-7+6-5+4*321$
2074	03544	$1234+56-(-7+8-9AB)$	$-B+A-98+7+6*(5-432)*-1$
2075	03545	$123+456*7+8*(-9-AB)$	$BA9+8+7-6-5+4*321$
2076	03546	$1+2+3*(-4-(-5+67)+89A-B)$	$-B-A+9-876-54*-3*21$
2077	03547	$1234-5-(6+7)*-89+AB$	$-BA-9-(8+7)-6*(-5-432)-1$
2078	03548	$-12-3*(4-5)*(-67+89A)-B$	$-B-A-9+8+(76-5)*A(4-32*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2079	03549	$1-2+34*56-7*(-8+9-AB)$	$BA9+8*-7*-6*5-4*(-32-1)$
207A	03550	$123+45*(-6+78)-9*AB$	$-B-A-98*-7-654*-3-21$
207B	03551	$1*(2-3)*45*(6+7*8-(9A+B))$	$BA9-8+7+6+5-4*-321$
2080	03552	$1*-2*-3*4*(-56-(-78+9-AB))$	$BA-9*-8*76+5*432*-1$
2081	03553	$-1*(234-5)*(-6-(7+8-(9-(A-B))))$	$B+A9-8+76*(5-4)*32+1$
2082	03554	$1-2-(-3+4+56*7*-8)-9-AB$	$-B-A-9*(8-7+6)*-54-321$
2083	03555	$-12+34+5*6*(7-8)*-9A-B$	$B-(A9-876-54*32+1)$
2084	03556	$-12*(345+6*7*-8-(9A-B))$	$B-(A9-876)-54*-32*1$
2085	03557	$-1-23-4-56*7*-8-(9A-B)$	$B-A9+876-(54*-32-1)$
2086	03558	$1234+56+7-8+9AB$	$B-A9-8-(7-654)*(3-(-2+1))$
2087	03559	$1234+56+7-(8-9AB)$	$-BA9+8-7*(-6-543+21)$
2088	03560	$1234+56-7+8+9AB$	$BA9-(8-7)+65*4*3*2*1$
2089	03561	$-1+2345-6-7*8*9+AB$	$-BA+987-6*-54*-3*-2*1$
208A	03562	$-1+2-34-5*-678+9*-AB$	$BA9-8*7+65-4*-321$
208B	03563	$-1+23*-4*(-56+7-89+AB)$	$BA9+876-(5-(432-1))$
2090	03564	$1234-5-6+78+9AB$	$-B*(A-9+8)*(-7+6)*(54-(3+21))$
2091	03565	$1234-5+6+7+8+9AB$	$BA9+876-5+432+1$
2092	03566	$1234-5-6*-7*8+9*AB$	$B+A*98+76+5*(4+321)$
2093	03567	$1+2+3+4+56*7-8*9A+B$	$BA9+87-65+4*321$
2094	03568	$1234-5+6*(7+8)+9AB$	$-B-A-9+8*76*5-4+3-2+1$
2095	03569	$1234-5*-6+7*8+9AB$	$BA9+8+(7-654-3)*-2*1$
2096	03570	$-12*3*(-4-56-(-78+9A)+B)$	$BA9+8-7-654*(-3+2-1)$
2097	03571	$1+2*34*(-5*-6+7+8)-9-A-B$	$B+A*98*7-6*5*-4*32*-1$
2098	03572	$1-2345-6*(7-89A+B)$	$B+A+9+8*7+6+(5-4*3)^2-1$
2099	03573	$-1+2/3*4*5*6*7/8-9+A-B$	$BA9+876-(5-432+1)$
209A	03574	$1234+56+7+8+9AB$	$BA9-(-876-5-432*1)$
209B	03575	$1234-(-5-67-8-9AB)$	$BA9+876+5+432+1$
20A0	03576	$1234-5-(-6-78-9AB)$	$B+A98-(-7+65*(-4+3-21))$
20A1	03577	$-123+4*(-56+789+A*-B)$	$BA-9-(8-76)*54+3-21$
20A2	03578	$12-34*-56+7*(-8+9+AB)$	$BA9+8+7+(654-3)*-2*-1$
20A3	03579	$1+2-3*-4*(56+78-(-9-AB))$	$-BA+9-8*(7-(654-321))$
20A4	03580	$1*2*(345+6-7+8+9A*B)$	$-B-(A-(-9-87))-(-6*(-5-432)+1)$
20A5	03581	$-12+3+4*(567-(8-9A+B))$	$B-A9-8-7+6*(5-432*-1)$
20A6	03582	$-1+2+(-34-5)*-67-89+AB$	$B+A-9*8*7-6*5+4*(3*2)-1$
20A7	03583	$1*2+3*4*5+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9*(87-65*-4+3)-2+1$
20A8	03584	$1+2345+6*7*8-9*A*B$	$B-(A-9)-(-8*-76*-5+4-(3-21))$
20A9	03585	$-12-3456-7-8*-9*AB$	$-BA-9*-8+7-6*(5-432+1)$
20AA	03586	$1234+5+6+7+8+9AB$	$B-A9+87*-6*-5+432*1$
20AB	03587	$-1-2-3*(-4-(56+789+A))+B$	$-B-A987+6543*2-1$
20B0	03588	$-1-23+4*(-567-89)*(A-B)$	$-B-A987+6543*-2*-1$
20B1	03589	$-1*(-23-4-56)*(-78+9A+B)$	$-B-A98*-7+65-4321$
20B2	03590	$-1*2*3*(4-56+7)*(-8+9)-A*-B)$	$-B+A*(98+76)-543*-2-1$
20B3	03591	$-123*(4-5+6+7+8-9A+B)$	$-BA-9-8+(-76-5*-4*3)*-21$
20B4	03592	$-12+3456+7+(8+9)*-AB$	$BA+9*(-8+7-6*-54)-3*(-2+1)$
20B5	03593	$1-2-3-4-5*-678-9*AB$	$B+A-9+8*7*(6-5)*4*3-2-1$
20B6	03594	$1-(2-3-4*(567-8+9A-B))$	$B-A-(98*-7+654*-3)-(-2+1)$
20B7	03595	$1*-2-3-4*5*-6*(-78-9+AB)$	$B+A*9+876-54*32*-1$
20B8	03596	$-1+23-4*5*(-67-89)-A*B$	$B+A*9*-8+7*(-6+5)*(-432-1)$
20B9	03597	$-1-(-2345+6*78+(-9-A)*B)$	$-B*(A9+8+7-(654-321))$
20BA	03598	$-1+2345+678-9A*B$	$-B-A9+876-54*(-32-1)$
20BB	03599	$-12-3456+7-8*9*-AB$	$BA+9+8*(-76+54+321)$
2100	03600	$1+2345+678+9A*-B$	$-BA-(9-876*(5-4)*3-21)$
2101	03601	$1^2+3*4^5/6*7+8+9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9+87-65*(43-2-1))$
2102	03602	$-123+45*(67-8)+9+A+B$	$-BA-9*(87-65)*4*(-3-2+1)$
2103	03603	$123+4*567-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A*9*-8-(-765*4+3)-(2+1)$
2104	03604	$12-3+4-56*-7*8-9A+B$	$B+A-9-8+(7-6-5+4^3)^2/1$
2105	03605	$-1-2*3456-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A98-7*6*-5-4*-321$
2106	03606	$1*2*3*(-4-5-(-6-7*89+AB))$	$B+A+(9+8)*7*6*5+4*3+2+1$
2107	03607	$1-(2-3)+4-(-5*678+9*AB)$	$-B-(A9+87-65*(43-2+1))$
2108	03608	$-12-34*-56+789-AB$	$-B*(A9-(8+76*5+4)+3-2*-1)$
2109	03609	$-1+234+5*-6*7*-8-9+AB$	$-BA9-8-7*(6-543)-21$
210A	03610	$12+34-56*7*-8-(9+AB)$	$-B+A9+(-87+6)*(-54+3+21)$
210B	03611	$1-23-4*(-567-89)+A+B$	$B+A*(-9-(8+7)-(-65-(4+321)))$
2110	03612	$1-234-5*6*-78+9*AB$	$B-(A+98)-(-7+6*(-5-(432+1)))$
2111	03613	$12-34*-56-(-78*9-AB)$	$-B-(-A-9+87+6*(-5-(432-1)))$
2112	03614	$-1-(-2+3456-7)+8*9*AB$	$BA9+87+6-54*(-3-21)$
2113	03615	$1234+56+7*8+9AB$	$BA-98*(-76+54)+321$
2114	03616	$12-3+4-5*-678+9*-AB$	$-BA-9-8*(-765+432)-1$
2115	03617	$-1-23*4*5+6*-7*(8-9A+B)$	$BA9-8-(-7-65+4*-321)$
2116	03618	$-1*2*3*(4+5)*(-6*-7-8+9*-A-B)$	$BA9-8+76-5+4*321$
2117	03619	$1-23-45*-6*7-8+9AB$	$-BA-(-9-8*76*5-4*32*1)$
2118	03620	$1+23-4*(-567+8-9A+B)$	$B+A+98*7+654*3+2+1$
2119	03621	$12+34-56*-7*8-9A-B$	$-B-A+9*8*7*6*5+4+32-1$
211A	03622	$-1-2*3*-456+7-89-AB$	$-BA-9*(-876+5)-4321$
211B	03623	$-123+4+5*678-9*-A*-B$	$-B-A9+87-6*(5-(432+1))$
2120	03624	$-1+2-34*-56+7*-8*(9-AB)$	$B+A-(98+765)*(4+3*-2-1)$
2121	03625	$-1-(-2345+67)-(89+AB)$	$-B+A+9-87+6*(5+432+1)$
2122	03626	$-1*(-2345+67-(-89-AB))$	$-B+A98-7*-65*4+3*-21$
2123	03627	$1-(-2345-(-67-89)+AB)$	$-BA+9+8-7*(65-432+1)$
2124	03628	$1*-2*(-345+6+78-9AB)$	$BA9-8+76+5-4*-321$
2125	03629	$-1-2*-34*56-7*(89+AB)$	$-B-A9+8*76*-5+4321$
2126	03630	$1*2*3*(456+78-9A-B)$	$-B+A*9-87*-6*5-(-4-321)$
2127	03631	$1234+5*(67+89+AB)$	$-BA+987+6+54*(32-1)$
2128	03632	$1-23*(-45-(6-7))+(-8-9)*-AB$	$-B-A9-8+(-7+65)*(43+2+1)$
2129	03633	$123+45*6+(-7-8-9)*-AB$	$BA9+87-6-(5-4*321)$
212A	03634	$-12-34-56*-7*8-9-A+B$	$-BA9-(8-7*(-6+543))*(2-1))$
212B	03635	$-1-2+345*6+7*(89+A-B)$	$-B+A-98-7*(65-(432-1))$
2130	03636	$12+34*56+789-AB$	$B+A-9-8*7+6*5-4*(3*2/1)$
2131	03637	$1-2-3+45*(67-8)+9-AB$	$-BA-(98+7-65*43+21)$
2132	03638	$-1*(-23-4+56+7-8)*(-9A+B)$	$B+A9+8*76*5-43*-2*-1$
2133	03639	$-1-2-3-45*6*-7-(8-9AB)$	$B+A+9+8+(7-6-5+4^3)^2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2134	03640	$-1*(23-(45-6))*7*(-89+AB)$	$BA-9+876-5*(4-321)$
2135	03641	$1-(-2+3)-45*(-67+8)-(-9+AB)$	$-BA+9+87*(-65+432+1)$
2136	03642	$12+3456-(-7+89*(A+B))$	$B-A9+8+7*(-65+432-1)$
2137	03643	$-1+2*34*5*-6-(-789-AB)$	$BA9+87-6+5-4*-321$
2138	03644	$1234-5-67+8*(-9-A)*-B$	$-B-(A-9)-8*7-654*(-3-2+1)$
2139	03645	$-1*23*(4-5)*(-6-7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A-9-(-876-54*32-1)$
213A	03646	$-1+2345-67-89+A*-B$	$-BA-9+(8-76)*(5-43)+21$
213B	03647	$1-(-2+34+56*7*8)-(-9+A)-B$	$-BA+98*-7+6*543-21$
2140	03648	$1234-56*7-8*(-9-AB)$	$-BA-9-87-65*-43-21$
2141	03649	$1-2345+6*(-7+89A)+B$	$B+A+9*8*7+(6-5+4)^(3+2)-1$
2142	03650	$1*2*(345-67-8+9AB)$	$-B-A9+8*76-5*-432*1$
2143	03651	$1234+56+78+9AB$	$-B-A-987+(6+5)*(4+321)$
2144	03652	$1*2*(345+6-(78-9AB))$	$-B*(A9-8+7+6-5-4-321)$
2145	03653	$-1+2-(34*-56+78*(-9+A))*-B$	$BA9+8+7+65*(-4+3)*-21$
2146	03654	$1-23+4*(567-(8-9A-B))$	$B+A+9-8*7+6^5-4^(3*2/1)$
2147	03655	$-12-34*(5+6+7+8-9A)-B$	$BA9+87+6+5+4*321$
2148	03656	$1+2-(3+45*(-67+8))-9A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7+6+5^4(4+3-2)^1$
2149	03657	$123+4-5*-678-9A*B$	$B+A+9*8*7+6+5^4(4+3-2)+1$
214A	03658	$-1-(23-456*7-8*(-9*A-B))$	$-B-A-9+87*6-5*432*-1$
214B	03659	$12+345*6-7*-89*(-A+B)$	$B-A-(-987+6-5*(-4+321))$
2150	03660	$1+2345-(67-8*-9)-AB$	$B+A*(9+87)*6-5*432-1$
2151	03661	$-1+2*-3*(-456+7)-8-9-AB$	$-B+A-(-9+8-7)+6*(-5+432)*1$
2152	03662	$1+2+3-(4-5*6*(7+8+9A-B))$	$-B-(-A98+7*65*-4+32+1)$
2153	03663	$1-2-(-34-5)*67+8-(9-A*B)$	$-B*(A9+8-765+432+1)$
2154	03664	$-1-(23-4)-(56*7*8-(-9-A))+B$	$-BA-98-7-65*-43-2*-1$
2155	03665	$-1*(-2-3)*(456+7+89-A-B)$	$-B+A9+876+5*(4+321)$
2156	03666	$-12-34*(5-6-(7+89)-(-A-B))$	$B-A-9+876+54*-32*-1$
2157	03667	$-12+3*4*(5-6*7)*-8+9A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6+5^4-3^A(2-1)$
2158	03668	$-1*(2-3-45-67+89)*AB$	$B-A-9-8*76*-5-(-43-21)$
2159	03669	$1+23*-45+6*78*9+AB$	$BA9+8*76*5+4-3*21$
215A	03670	$1+2+3+4*(-56+789-AB)$	$BA9+87*(-6+54-32-1)$
215B	03671	$1-2*-3-4*(56-789+AB)$	$B-A-9-8*-76*5+4-3*-21$
2160	03672	$12-(3+45*-6*7-(8+9AB))$	$-BA+9*876+5-4321$
2161	03673	$-123-4*5-(-67-89)*(A+B)$	$-BA-98+7+65*43-2-1$
2162	03674	$-1+2^A(3*4)-5/6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9-8*-7+65-4*-321$
2163	03675	$1*2^A(3*4)-5/6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-B+A9-87+6*(-5+432+1)$
2164	03676	$1+2^A(3*4)-5/6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA-9+87+6*(5+432)-1$
2165	03677	$-1-23-4567-8*-9AB$	$-BA-(98-(7-65*-43+2))-1$
2166	03678	$1*-23-4567+8*9AB$	$-B-(-A-987+6*5*(-43-21))$
2167	03679	$1-23-4567*-8*-9AB$	$B+A*9+8+(-76+5)*(-4-32*1)$
2168	03680	$1234-56-7*-8*(9+A+B)$	$-B+A*9*(8-(-7-65+43))+2-1$
2169	03681	$-1*(-234+5*-678+9AB)$	$B-A*9+8+7*(-65+432-1)$
216A	03682	$1*-2*(-345+67-8-9AB)$	$-B-A*9+8-(76+54-3)*-21$
216B	03683	$-1+2345-(-6*-7+89-A*-B)$	$-BA-(-987+6+54*32*-1)$
2170	03684	$1+23-(-45*(-67+8))-(-9A+B)$	$B-(-A98-7*65*4+32+1)$
2171	03685	$-1*(-2/-3-4^5*6)/(7+8)*9+A-B$	$B*(A9+87-(-65-4)-(-3-21))$
2172	03686	$-1+23+(-4+56-78)*(9-AB)$	$-BA-9*8-(-7-6)*5(5+4+3)*21$
2173	03687	$12-345-6*-7*(-8+9A-B)$	$-B-A-9*(87-(-6+54+321))$
2174	03688	$1-(-23+4*-5*(67+89+A-B))$	$-BA-9-(-8*7+65*(-43+2)+1)$
2175	03689	$1+23+45*6*7*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A9-8*76*-5-43*(2-1)$
2176	03690	$-1*(-2-3)*(4-5-(-67*8-9A+B))$	$B-A*(-9-8+7+6)*(-5+43)*2-1$
2177	03691	$-1+2345-(6-(-7-89))-AB$	$BA-9-876+54*-3*-21$
2178	03692	$-1*(-2345+6+7+89+AB)$	$-B+A987-6*54*(32+1)$
2179	03693	$1+2345-(6+7)-(89+AB)$	$B-A+9*87*-6+5432*1$
217A	03694	$-12+3-4567-8*-9AB$	$-BA-(-987-6-54*32+1)$
217B	03695	$-1-(-2+34*56)-(7-89*A)+B$	$-B+A+9*8+(-7-6+5)*4-321$
2180	03696	$1*-2*3*(4-(-567-8+9AB))$	$-BA-9*-8-7*(-65-4-321)$
2181	03697	$1+2345-6*7-8*9-AB$	$-B-(-A9+8*-76*5+(-4-3)*(-2-1))$
2182	03698	$-1+2*-3-4567-8*-9AB$	$BA+9+876+5*(4+321)$
2183	03699	$-1*23*(-4+56-78-9A+B)$	$B+A9+87+6*54*3*(2+1)$
2184	03700	$-1*2*(3*-4-567-89*A+B)$	$-B-A-9+(-8+7+6)*(543-21)$
2185	03701	$1-2-3-4567-8*-9AB$	$BA9+876+543-21$
2186	03702	$-1+2345-(6+78+9+AB)$	$-B-A+9-8+7-6*(-5-432)+1$
2187	03703	$-1+2345+6-7-89-AB$	$B+A+9-(-876-54*32)-1$
2188	03704	$1+2345-(6-(-78-(9+AB)))$	$B+A9*-8-(-7+6+54)*-3*21$
2189	03705	$-1-2+3-(4567+8*-9AB)$	$B-A-9*8*-7+(65+43)*21$
218A	03706	$12-34*-56+7+(89-A)*B$	$-B-A9-8*7+65*43-21$
218B	03707	$1-(-2345+6-7)-(89+AB)$	$B*(-A9-8+7*(65-4)-32+1)$
2190	03708	$1-2+345*-6-7*8*-9A+B$	$B+A-9-8*7+6*5^4+3-2+1$
2191	03709	$1-2*-3*4+56*7*8-(-9-(-A-B))$	$-B-A9-8+7-65*(-43-(-2+1))$
2192	03710	$1234+5*67+89A-B$	$-BA9+8*(-76+543)-21$
2193	03711	$-1+2345-6*-7*-8-(-9A+B)$	$-B-(A9+8*7*-65)-(-4+321)$
2194	03712	$1-2*-3-4567-8*-9AB$	$-B+A+9+87*6*5+432*1$
2195	03713	$-1+2345-6-78-9A-B$	$-B+A9+8*-76*-5-4-3+2*1$
2196	03714	$-1*(-2345+6+78+9A+B)$	$-BA-9+(87-(6+5))*(4+32)+1$
2197	03715	$1+2345-(67+8+9)-AB$	$-B+A+98+76*(5-(-4-32)+1)$
2198	03716	$1*2*(-3-4*-5*(-6-(7-89)))-(-A-B))$	$-BA-(-9+87-65*43-21)$
2199	03717	$-1+2345+6+7-89-AB$	$-B+A9+8*76*5*(-4+3+2)-1$
219A	03718	$-1-(-2345-6*(78-(9A+B)))$	$B*(-A-9-87-(6-5-4)+321)$
219B	03719	$1+2345+678-9*AB$	$-BA9+8*-7*(6-(54+32+1))$
21A0	03720	$-1*(-2-3)*(-4+56)*(7-89-A*-B)$	$-B+A+9+8*(-7+654-321)$
21A1	03721	$-1-(-2+34+5*(-6+78)*-9)-A*B$	$-BA+987-65*(-4-3-21)$
21A2	03722	$1+2345-67+8*(-9-A)+B$	$B+A-9+8+7*(6+5+4*3)^2-1$
21A3	03723	$1-2+34-5*(-6-7*89)-A-B$	$BA9+876+543-(2+1)$
21A4	03724	$-1*-2*(345+6-7*8+9AB)$	$B+A+987+6*-54*3*2*-1$
21A5	03725	$-1*(-2345+6+7+8-(-9A-B))$	$BA9+876+543-(2-1)$
21A6	03726	$1+2345-67-8-9A-B$	$-BA+98-7*(65-432+1)$
21A7	03727	$1-(-2345-6)-78-9A-B$	$BA9+876+543-(-2+1)$
21A8	03728	$1+2*-3-45*67+8*-9*-A*B$	$B-(-A-(-9-8*7-65*(-43+2)))+1$
21A9	03729	$-1+2345-(67-8)-(9+AB)$	$-B+A98-(-7-65)*(43-21)$
21AA	03730	$-1+23+4*(567+8-(-9A*B))$	$BA9+8-(-7-65*(43-21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
21AB	03731	1+2345-67+8-9-AB	-B-A9+8*-7-65*43*(-2+1)
21B0	03732	-1+2345+6-78+9-AB	B+A9-(-8*-7-6*(-5+432-1))
21B1	03733	-1+2+34*56+789-A-B	B+A+98*(76-54+3+2+1)
21B2	03734	1+2345+6-78+9-AB	-B+A*(-9-8+7-6*-54)+3+2*1
21B3	03735	-1+2345-67-89-A-B	-B-A9+(-8-(-7-65))*43-2+1
21B4	03736	-1*(-2345+6-(-78-9A)-B)	-B-A98-76*-54-321
21B5	03737	1+2345-67-89-A-B	-B+A9*8-7*6*-54+3+21
21B6	03738	-1*-2*-3*(-456-7-(89-AB))	-B-A-9-8*(-765+432)*1
21B7	03739	12+34-56*7*-8*(-9+A)-B	-B+A98-(-765+4*-3)*2*1
21B8	03740	1+2345-6+7*-8-9-AB	-BA+98-7*(65-432-1)
21B9	03741	1+2*34-5*6*(-78-(9+A)-B)	-B+A-9-8-7*(65-432*1)
21BA	03742	1+2345-67+8-9A-B	B+A98-76-5*(4-321)
21BB	03743	1+2345-6-78+9+A*-B	-BA+9+87+65*(43-2)*1
2200	03744	1+2345+6*(-7+89-AB)	B-(A+9+8*-7*(65-4-(3+2+1)))
2201	03745	1*(-23-4-5+67-8)*(9A-B)	-BA+9*-87*-6-(54+3)*21
2202	03746	-1+2345-67-8-9A+B	-B-A-98+765*4-321
2203	03747	-1-(-2345+67-8-9)-AB	-B+A-98*7-6*-5*-4*32*-1
2204	03748	1+2345-67-8-(9A-B)	-BA-98*-7-(-65-4)*-32*-1
2205	03749	1+2345-(67-8)-(-9+AB)	BA+9-8*-76*5+4+3*-2*1
2206	03750	-1+2345+6+7*-8-9-AB	B-(-A+9)+876+54*(32+1)
2207	03751	-1-2*(3+45)+(-67-89)*(-A-B)	-B-(A9-8)-765*-4-321
2208	03752	-1*(23+4*(-5-(678-9-A)))-B)	-BA9-(87-654*-3*-2*1)
2209	03753	1*2345-67-89+A*-B	B-A+(-9+8)*7*(65-432+1)
220A	03754	-1-23*-4+(56-7)*(8*9-A)-B	B-A-(-9+8)-7*(65-432+1)
220B	03755	-1-(-2345+67+89-A)-B	BA+9+8*76*5+4+3+2+1
2210	03756	-1-2-3*(-45+6+78-9A*B)	BA+9+8*76*5+4+3-2*1
2211	03757	-1*(2345-67-89)*(A-B)	-B+A98+7+(-6+54)*32+1
2212	03758	123-4*(-567-89+A)+B	B-A98-76*-54-321
2213	03759	-1-(-2345-(6-(7-8*-9-A*-B)))	-BA9+8*(-76+543+2+1)
2214	03760	1*-2*(-3*(45+6+78)-9AB)	-B+A+987-(6+54*(-32+1))
2215	03761	-1+2345-(-6-7*-8)-(9A+B)	BA+9+876-54*(-32+1)
2216	03762	1*(-234-5+6-7-8*(-9+A))*-B	-B*(A9-(-8+7+6+5)-4-321)
2217	03763	-1-(234-56*(78-9-(A+B)))	-B-(A9-8)-(-7+65*-43+21)
2218	03764	1+2345-67-(-8+9A-B)	-BA-9+(8+765)*4-321
2219	03765	-123-(4+5*-6*(7+8)*9)-A*B	B+A-(-9+8+7)*(-6-(5+432-1))
221A	03766	-12+3*(4+56+7-8-9)*(A+B)	-BA-9+8-(-7+65*-43)-21
221B	03767	1+2345-67-8*(-9-(A-B))	B+A+9-8-7+6*5^4+3-2+1
2220	03768	-1-(-2345+67-8-9*-A)-B	BA+9-87-6*(-5-432-1)
2221	03769	1+2345-(-6*-7-(-8+9)*-AB)	B+A-98*7-6*5*-4*-32*-1
2222	03770	-1-(-2345-6)-(-7*-8-9+AB)	B+A+9-8-7+6*5^4+3+2+1
2223	03771	-12-(3-4*(567+8+9+AB))	BA9-8*-7+65*(43-21)
2224	03772	-1+2^3(3^4)+5-6*7*8+9+A-B	-B-A9-(8+7)+65*-43*(-2+1)
2225	03773	1+2345-6-7*8-9A+B	-B*(A-9-8)*7(-6-5-4)+32+1
2226	03774	1*-2*(-3-456-7*-8+9A*-B)	B-A-(-987-6)-54*(-32+1)
2227	03775	-1-2+3*-4+5*678-9*-A*-B	B-A+(98-7-6-(5-4))*(32-1)
2228	03776	1-2*(34+5)*-6*7+89+A*-B	-B+A+98+7-6*(5+432*-1)
2229	03777	-1-(-2345-(-67-89+A+B))	-B-A*9+8-76*(5-43+2+1)
222A	03778	1-2-3+(456-7)*8+9A*-B	-BA-(-9+8)-(-7-65*43)-2+1
222B	03779	1+2345-67-89+A+B	BA+9+8*76*5+4*(3*2+1)
2230	03780	-1*-2*(3+456-7*89)*(-A-B)	-BA+9-(8+7)-(-65*43-2+1)
2231	03781	1+2345-(6+7)-(-8+9+AB)	-B-A-9+87-6*(-5-432+1)
2232	03782	1234-(5-6*78)+9*AB	B+A+987-(6+54*(-32+1))
2233	03783	-1+2345+67-(89+AB)	B-A-9-8+7-(-65*43+21)
2234	03784	-1+2-3-4-(5*-678-9*A*-B)	B*(-A9+876-543+2*1)
2235	03785	1+2345+67-89-AB	B-A*(-9+8+7+6*54)+3*-2*1
2236	03786	123+4*(567-8*-9)+AB	B-A+9+8*(765-432+1)
2237	03787	-1*(2345+6*(-7-89A-B))	BA+9*(8-7-6)*(-5-43-21)
2238	03788	1234+567-(8*-9A+B)	BA9+8+(765-43)*2-1
2239	03789	-123-4*-56*(-78+9A-B)	-B-(-A-9)+8+7*65*(4+3)*(2-1)
223A	03790	-1-(-2345+6)-(7+8+9A+B)	B+A98-76+543*(2+1)
223B	03791	1*2345+6-(7+8)*9-A-B	-B+A9+876+54*32-1
2240	03792	1234+5-(6+78*(-9-A)+B)	B+A+9*-8-7+65*(43-2+1)
2241	03793	-1+2345-6+7-8-9-AB	-B-A+9*876+5-4321
2242	03794	-1+2345-6*7-89-A+B	B+A-(-987-6-54*(32-1))
2243	03795	-1-(-2345-(-6-7+8))-(-9-AB))	-B-A-9-87-(65*43-(2-1))
2244	03796	1*-2*(345-678-9AB)	-BA-98*-7-6*(-54-321)
2245	03797	1+2345-6-(7-8+9+AB)	-B-A9-8-7-65*-43+21
2246	03798	-1*(-2+3-4)*(-5+6)*(7+89A-B)	-BA+9+8-7-65*-43+2+1
2247	03799	-1-(-2345+6)-(7+8-9+AB)	BA+9-8*-76*5+43-2-1
2248	03800	1*(2-34)*-5*(-67-8-(-9A+B))	BA+9-(-8-(7+65)-4)*32+1
2249	03801	1+2345+6*-7+8-9A+B	-B-(-A9-87*6+5*(-432+1))
224A	03802	-1+2345+6-7-8-9A-B	B+A*-9*-8*(7-6)+5*432+1
224B	03803	-1+2*3*456+78-9-AB	B-A-98-7-65*-43-2*1
2250	03804	1234+5*-6*(-7-8)-9A*-B	-B-(A-(987-6-54*32*-1))
2251	03805	12-3+4*(-5+678)-9+A-B	-B+A*9-876*(5-4-(3+2)+1)
2252	03806	1+2345-6+7-8-(9A+B)	BA-98-76*(-54-3+21)
2253	03807	1+2345-(-6-7)-(-8+9)-AB	-B+A+9-87+65*43-21
2254	03808	12-345+6*7*89-AB	-BA+9-(-8-7)-(-65*-43+2-1)
2255	03809	1234+56*7+89A+B	-BA+9*(8-76+54+321)
2256	03810	1234+567-8*-9A+B	BA-9*8+(-7-654)*(-3-2+1)
2257	03811	1+234+5*678-9A*B	-B+A-9-87-65*-43-2-1
2258	03812	-1+2345-6-7-8-9A+B	-B+A+(987-(65+43))*(2+1)
2259	03813	-1-(-2345-6-(-7-89))-A-B	-B+A+98*-7-6*543*(-2+1)
225A	03814	1+2345-(6+7)-(8-(-9A+B))	-B+A9-8*(-7-6-54)*(3+2+1)
225B	03815	1-23*-45+678+9AB	B+A9+876-54*-32+1
2260	03816	1*-2*3*4*(5*-67-(-89-AB))	-B-(A-987)-(-6+54*32*-1)
2261	03817	1+2345-(6-(7-89-A-B))	-B*(-A-(-98-(7-(-6-(-5-4))))+321))
2262	03818	1+2345+6+7-8-9A-B	BA9+87-65*(43+21)
2263	03819	-123-45*-67-8+9*(-A-B)	-B+A-9*-8*7*6+543+21
2264	03820	-1*(-2-3)*(456+7+8-(-9A+B))	B+A-9+8*7+6*5^4+3-2+1
2265	03821	-1+2345+6+7+8-9-AB	B+A-9+8*7+6*5^4+3^2(2-1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2266	03822	$1 - (-2345 - (-6+7)) + 8 - (9A+B)$	$-BA+98^* - 7 - 6^* (-543-21)$
2267	03823	$-1+2345-67-8-9-(A+B)$	$-B-A98+7^*-65^*(-4-3^*2)^*1$
2268	03824	$12-34-5^*(-67+8-9+A)^*B$	$BA+9+876+54^*32-1$
2269	03825	$-1+2345-(-6+7)+8-(-9+A+B)$	$BA+9+876+54^*32^*-1$
226A	03826	$1+2345+6-7-(8+9A)+B$	$BA-9+87^*6-5^*(-432-1)$
226B	03827	$-1-(-2345-6-7)-(89-(-A-B))$	$B-(A-987+6-54^*32-1)$
2270	03828	$-1+2345-(6+7)-(-8+9A-B)$	$-B+A-(98+7)-65^*-43+21$
2271	03829	$-1^*(-2345+6+7-8-(-9A+B))$	$B+A+9^*8-7+6^*5^4-3^*2-1$
2272	03830	$1234-56+(-7-8)^*(9-A-B)$	$BA-9+8-7+65^*(43-2-1)$
2273	03831	$-1+2345-6-(78+(9-A)^*-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6+5^4*3^*2+1$
2274	03832	$-1+2345+6-(-7-8)-9A-B$	$BA-9-8^*-7^*65-432+1$
2275	03833	$1^*2345-6-78-9+A-B$	$B-A+9-87-65^*-43-(2-1)$
2276	03834	$1+2345-6-78-9+A-B$	$BA-9+8^*76^*5-43^*-2-1$
2277	03835	$-1+2345-67-(-89+A+B)$	$-B+A-(-987-6)-(-54^*-32+1)$
2278	03836	$1^*2^*(3-4^*-567-89A-B)$	$B-A9^*-8-7^*(-6+54-321)$
2279	03837	$1+2345-67+89-AB$	$-B-(-A-987-6-54^*32-1)$
227A	03838	$1^*-2^*(-345-(6-7+8+9AB))$	$BA9+8-7^*-65^*4-32-1$
227B	03839	$1+2345-(6-(7-89))-(-A-B)$	$B^*(-A9+8+765-432-1)$
2280	03840	$1^*-2+3-4567-89^*A^*B$	$BA+9^*-87+6^*543-(2-1)$
2281	03841	$-1-2^*-3^*456-(7-8)^*-9-(-A+B)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*-7^*-6-(-543-21)$
2282	03842	$-12+3-45-6^*-7^*(-8-(9^*A-B))$	$-B+A98-7+6^*-54^*3^*2^*-1$
2283	03843	$1+2345-(67+8-9-(-A-B))$	$-B-(A9+8^*-7+65^*43^*(-2+1))$
2284	03844	$1+2345-(-6+78-9)-(-A+B)$	$B+A+9^*8+7+6^*5^4-3^*2^*1$
2285	03845	$1-(-2345+67)-8-(9-A+B)$	$B+A98-(-76^*5+4^*-321)$
2286	03846	$-1^*(-2345+67+8+9+A-B)$	$BA+987+6^*-54^*3^*-2+1$
2287	03847	$-1-2345^*(6-7)+8-9^*A-B$	$-B-A+9-8^*7^*-65+4-321$
2288	03848	$-1+2345-(6-7)-8^*9-A-B$	$BA9-8^*76^*(-5+4)^*3-21$
2289	03849	$1+2345+6+7-89+A-B$	$BA9+8+7^*65^*4-3-21$
228A	03850	$-1^*2^*(3+4+56-(-7-89+A))^*-B$	$-B^*A^*(-9+8^*-7-6+54-3-21)$
228B	03851	$-1^*(-2345-(-6-78+9+A-B))$	$-B+A98+7-6-5^*(-4-321)$
2290	03852	$-1+2345-(6+78-9)-A+B$	$BA+987+6+5^*(4+321)$
2291	03853	$1234+567+8-9^*-A^*B$	$BA+98^*(76-5-43-2)-1$
2292	03854	$-1^*2^*(3-456-(7+89A)-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7-65+321)$
2293	03855	$-12+345^*6-78^*-9+AB$	$BA9-8-7^*-65^*4-3-2-1$
2294	03856	$-1+2345-67-(-89+A^*B)$	$-BA9+8-7+65^*4^*(3-(-2-1))$
2295	03857	$-1+2345-6+7-89-(-A-B)$	$-BA+98-765^*-4-321$
2296	03858	$1-2345^*(6-7)-(89-A)+B$	$B-(-A-987-6)+54^*32^*1$
2297	03859	$-1-(-2345-(-67+8)+9-(A-B))$	$-BA+9^*-8-7^*6^*(5-43^*2)-1$
2298	03860	$1^*(-2-3)^*(-456+7-8-9A-B)$	$BA-(9-8-7)+65^*(3+2-1)$
2299	03861	$-1+2345-67-(8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A+98+7^*(65+4+321)$
229A	03862	$-1+2345+6-78+9+A-B$	$BA-(9-(8+7)-6^*(-5-432))^*-1$
229B	03863	$1+2345-67+8-9-(A-B)$	$-B-A-(-9-87)+65^*(43-2)-1$
22A0	03864	$-12^*-3^*(45-(-6-7+89)+AB)$	$B+A98-7+6^*54^*3^*2^*1$
22A1	03865	$-1+23-4567-89^*A^*B$	$-BA-(9+87-6-(5+4)^*321)$
22A2	03866	$-1^*-2^*(345+6+7+8+9AB)$	$B+A-9+8+7+6^*5^4*3^*2-1$
22A3	03867	$-1^*(-23-4^*(-5+678+9))^*(-A+B)$	$B-A-9-(8+765^*-4)-321$
22A4	03868	$1^*-2^*(3+4+5-678+9^*-A^*B)$	$BA9+8-7^*65^*-4-3^*(2+1)$
22A5	03869	$1+2345+6-7-8^*-9^*(A-B)$	$BA-98-7-65^*(-43+2-1)$
22A6	03870	$1-2^*-3^*(456-7-8)+9A-B$	$-B+A9-(8^*76^*-5+4^*-32^*1)$
22A7	03871	$1^*2345-6-(-7-8)-(-9^*-A-B)$	$BA-9+876-54^*(-32-1)$
22A8	03872	$-1+2345-(6+78-9-(-A+B))$	$-BA+9^*(876-543-21)$
22A9	03873	$1+2345+67-8-9-AB$	$BA9-87^*-6+543^*-2^*-1$
22AA	03874	$1+2345-6-78+9+A+B$	$-B-(-A-98-7^*(65-432))^*-1$
22AB	03875	$1^*(-2-3)^*(-456-7-89-A-B)$	$-B+A+98+7^*(-65+432)+1$
22B0	03876	$123-4567+8^*9AB$	$-BA-9+(876+543)^*2+1$
22B1	03877	$-12+345-(-67+89)^*-AB$	$BA9+8-7^*65^*-4-3+2+1$
22B2	03878	$-12-34^*-56-7+89A-B$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6-543^*-2^*-1$
22B3	03879	$-123+45^*67-(8+9A+B)$	$-B-A+9+8+765^*4-321$
22B4	03880	$-1+23+4+5^*(-67-8^*-9)^*-A^*B$	$-B-A^*-98+7^*6^*(54-(-3+2))+1$
22B5	03881	$12+3^*(4-5)^*(-67+(8-9A)^*B)$	$-B+A-9+8-765^*-4-321$
22B6	03882	$1+2345+6-(7^*-8-9)-AB$	$B-A+9+8^*(7+6^*5+4+321)$
22B7	03883	$1+2345-67+8-9+A+B$	$B-A-9+8+765^*4-321$
22B8	03884	$1+2345+67-(8+9A)-B$	$-BA9+876^*5-432+1$
22B9	03885	$1+2345-67-8+9+A+B$	$-B+A98-76^*(54-32)^*-1$
22BA	03886	$1-(-2345-6-(-78+9)-A)+B$	$BA-9^*8^*(-7-65+4-(-3-21))$
22BB	03887	$-1-(-2345-67-8-(-9-AB))$	$B-A9+87+65^*43-21$
2300	03888	$1^*-23^*(-4-5+6+7-8-9-AB)$	$-B-(-A-(987-6)+54^*(-32-1))$
2301	03889	$-1+2345+67-8+9-AB$	$B-(-A-9)-(8^*-7^*65-4+321)$
2302	03890	$12+34-56^*7^*-8+9+AB$	$BA9-87-6^*5^*(-43-21)$
2303	03891	$1+2345-(-67+8-9)-AB$	$-B-A9+87-65^*-43+2-1$
2304	03892	$1^*-2^*(34-567-8-9^*AB)$	$-B+A^*9+(-8-(76-5))^*(-4-(-32-1))$
2305	03893	$-1+2345+67-89-(A+B)$	$-B-A98+7^*6^*5^*(43-21)$
2306	03894	$-1^*(-2345-67+89+A+B)$	$-B^*(-A9-87^*6-(54-321))$
2307	03895	$-1-(-2345-6+7^*-8+9A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9+8+7)-(65^*-43+21)$
2308	03896	$-12+34+5^*6^*(-7+8)^*(9A+B)$	$-BA+9+8+7+65^*43-(2-1)$
2309	03897	$-1+2345-6+78-9A-B$	$-BA+9+87-65^*43^*(-2+1)$
230A	03898	$-1+2345+6-(-78+9+AB)$	$BA9+8^*-76^*(5+4)^*3+21$
230B	03899	$-12+345^*6+789-A^*B$	$BA+987+6^*(-5+321)$
2310	03900	$-1^*2^*(-345-67+(-8-9A)^*B)$	$BA-9-8-(76+54-3)^*21$
2311	03901	$-1+2345-6-(7-89)-AB$	$-B+A9^*8^*-7+6543-(2+1)$
2312	03902	$-123+45^*67-(-8-9)-AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6^*(-5+432-1)$
2313	03903	$1-(-2345+6+7-89+AB)$	$BA+987-6-54^*(-32+1)$
2314	03904	$-1+2345-(-67+8)-(9A-B)$	$B-A-98^*(-7-(6+5^*4))+3^*21$
2315	03905	$-1-(-2345-67-8-(9-AB))$	$-B+A98+765+43^*21$
2316	03906	$-12^*(-3-4+5+6+7+8+9-AB)$	$B-A-9-8-7-65^*-43-2^*-1$
2317	03907	$-1^*(-2345-678-9^*A^*B)$	$BA-9+8+7^*(65+4+321)$
2318	03908	$1+2345+678-9^*A^*B$	$-BA+98+7+65^*43^*(2-1)$
2319	03909	$1+2345-6-7-8-(-9+A)-B$	$B-(-A98+76)+54^*32^*1$
231A	03910	$1-23^*-45+(-6-(7+89))^*(-A-B)$	$B-A^*(-98+7)-(-654^*3-21)$
231B	03911	$1+2345+6+78-9A-B$	$-B-(-A-9-8)-(-7+65^*-43+21)$
2320	03912	$1+2345+67-8+9+A^*-B$	$BA+98-7^*(-6+5^*-43)^*-2^*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2321	03913	-1+2345-(-67+89-A)-B	-B+A-(9+8)-(-7+65*-43)-2-1
2322	03914	1+2+3+4*5+6+7+8-9*-AB	B-(-A+98*-7-6)-5*(-432-1)
2323	03915	-1+2345-(6-7)-(-89+AB)	BA+987+6-54*(-32+1)
2324	03916	-1*(-2345-67+89+A-B)	B*(-A98+7+65+4*321)
2325	03917	1+2345+67-89-(A-B)	B+A+9-8-7-65*-43-21
2326	03918	1+2345+6-(-78-9)-AB	B+A98-7-6*(54-321)
2327	03919	-1+2345-(6-78+9A-B)	-BA+98-(7+65*-43-21)
2328	03920	-1-(-2345-67-8)-(9A-B)	BA+9-(-8*76*-5-4321)
2329	03921	1-(-2345+6-(78-9A)-B)	-B-A9-8*76*-5-(-4-321)
232A	03922	1+2345-(-67-8+9A-B)	-BA+9+87-(65*-43-21)
232B	03923	-1-(-2345+6*-7)-8*-9-AB	B+A+9+8+(7-6+5)^4*3-2-1
2330	03924	1+2-3*(45-67-89A-B)	B+A+9+8+(7-6+5)^4*3-2^1
2331	03925	1+2345-6*(-7-8)-9A+B	BA9+8*-7+(65+4)*(3+21)
2332	03926	-1-(-2345-67)-(-8-9+A*B)	-B-A98-76*(-54+3)-(-2-1)
2333	03927	-1+2345+6+7+89-AB	B+A98+765+43*21
2334	03928	-12+3*(4+5+6+789+AB)	B-A9*(8+7)-65*(-43-21)
2335	03929	-1+2345-6-7-8+9-A+B	B+A-(9-8-(7+65*43)+21)
2336	03930	1-(-234+5*-678-9*-AB)	B+A98-7-6*5*(-4+3*-21)
2337	03931	-1+2345+6+7+8-9A+B	BA-98*7+6*543-21
2338	03932	-1-23-4*-5*-6*(-7-(-89+AB))	B+A98*(76-54*-3*-2*-1)
2339	03933	1+2345+6+7+8-9-A-B	-BA+98+7+65*43+21
233A	03934	-1+2345+6*(-7+8)+9-A-B	-BA-98*7*-6-543-21
233B	03935	-1+2345-(-67+89-A)+B	-BA9-8*(76-543-21)
2340	03936	-1*234*(-5+6)*(7-8)*(-9+A+B)	-B+A+(-98+76*-5)*(-4-3)-21
2341	03937	1-(-2345-67)-(89-A-B)	BA+9*8*7*6-543*(-2+1)
2342	03938	-1-2-3+4-5*6*(7+8)*-9-A*B	BA+9*(8-76*-5-4)-3-(2+1)
2343	03939	1+2345-(-6-78)+9+A*-B	B-(-A9-(-87-65*-43-21))
2344	03940	-1+2345+6*7*(-8+9+A-B)	-B+A98+76+5*(4+321)
2345	03941	-12+3-45*(-67+8)+9*(A+B)	-B-(-A+9)-(8-7-(-65*-43+21))
2346	03942	-1+2+(3-4+5+6)*-78-9A+B	B+A-9*(8-7)+65*43-(-2-1)
2347	03943	-1+2345-(6+78)-(9-A*B)	B+A-(-9-(-8-7))-(-65*43-2+1)
2348	03944	-1*(-2345-(6-(7+8)-(9-A))-B)	B-A98-76*(-54+3)-2+1
2349	03945	1-2-3+5+6*7*89+A+B	-BA-98-(-76+(-5-4)*321)
234A	03946	1-(-2345+6*-7)-8*-9-A*B	B-A+(-98+7+65+4+3)*(-2-1)
234B	03947	1+2345-67+89-A-B	BA+98+7*(6+5+4+3+2+1)
2350	03948	-12*-3*(-4+5+6-7+8)-(-9-AB))	-B-A-98*-7+65*(4+32-1)
2351	03949	1+2345-6-7+8-9+A+B	B*(-A+9+8+7+65*4+32-1)
2352	03950	-1*-2*(34-(-5+67*-8)-9A*-B)	BA+9-87-65*-43-21
2353	03951	1+2345-6-78+9A-B	-B-A*-9*8+7-65*(-4-32)+1
2354	03952	-1+23-4*(5-678)-9+AB	BA9+8+7*-6*-54-321
2355	03953	-1+2345-6-7-89+AB	BA9+8*7*(-6+5+4+32-1)
2356	03954	12+34-5*-6*(-7+8+9A+B)	-BA+9+8*-7*(-65+4)-(-3+2)*-1
2357	03955	-1+2345-(-6-7+8)-(-9+A)+B	-B+A*-9+(87-65)*4*(32+1)
2358	03956	1+2345-67-8+9*A+B	B+A-(-9-(8-7))+65*43-2*1
2359	03957	1+2345+6+7-8-(-9+A)+B	-BA9+87+654*3*2-1
235A	03958	-1+2345+6+(7-8)*9+A+B	B+A*9*8+7*(-6+5)*(-4-321)
235B	03959	-1+2345-(-6-78-(-9*A+B))	-B+A+9-8+7-(65*-43-21)
2360	03960	-1*-2*-3*-4*(-5-6)*(78-(9A-B))	BA-9-87+65*43+2+1
2361	03961	1-2*-3*456-(7-8-9A)-B	-B+A-(-9-8)-(7-65*43-21)
2362	03962	1+2345-(6+7*-8)-(9-(-A-B))	B-A9-8+7+65*(43-2*-1)
2363	03963	1+2345+6-78+9A-B	-B+A98-(7+6)-(-54*32+1)
2364	03964	-1+2345-(6+78+9-AB)	-B+A98-7-6-54*32*-1
2365	03965	-1+2345+6-7-89+AB	-BA9+8-76*(-54+3-2*1)
2366	03966	1+2345-(6+78)-9+AB	B-A9-8*-7*(65-4)-(3+2-1)
2367	03967	-1+2345-67+89-A+B	BA+987-6-54*-32*1
2368	03968	-1-(-2345-6)-(-78-9*-A)*B	BA+987-6-54*-32+1
2369	03969	1+2345-6+7-89+AB	-B+A9-(-8+765)*-4-321
236A	03970	-1*(-2345-(6+7)-(-8-9-A+B))	B+A+987+6*(5+4*3)*21
236B	03971	-1-(-2345+6+78-9A-B)	BA9+8-76*-5*(4-(-3-2*-1))
2370	03972	-1-2+3-45*-67-89-A*B	BA+98*(7-6*-5-4)-(-3+2-1)
2371	03973	1+2345-6-78+9A+B	-BA-98-76*(-5-4-32)+1
2372	03974	-1-(-2345+678+9*A*-B)	BA+9-87+65*43-2+1
2373	03975	1+2345-(-6-7)-(-8+9)+A+B	BA9-8*-76+543*2*1
2374	03976	-1-(-2345+67-8)-(-9A+B)	BA*(-9+8)*(-7*-6-54-3*-2*-1)
2375	03977	1+2345-(67+8+9)+AB	B+A98+7*6+54*(32-1)
2376	03978	1+2345-67+8+9A-B	BA-(-9+87-65*43-2-1)
2377	03979	1+2345+6*7+89-A*B	B-A9*(-87+65)-432*-1
2378	03980	-1-2*-3*-456*(7-8)-(-9A-B)	BA+9*8-7+65*(43+2*-1)
2379	03981	1+2345-6-7*-8-(-9A)*B	B-(-A-9+8-7+65*-43-21)
237A	03982	-1+2345-67-(8-(9A+B))	-BA-9*-8*-7-6*-543+2*1
237B	03983	-12+345*6-78-9*-AB	BA9-8-76+54*(32-1)
2380	03984	1+2345-67-8+9A+B	-BA-98*7*-6-543+21
2381	03985	1-(-2345-6-(-78+9A+B))	B+A98-7-6-54*-32-1
2382	03986	-12+34*5*6*(67+8-9A+B)	-B+A9*(8+76-54-3)-2*1
2383	03987	-1+234+5*6*(7-8)*(9-AB)	B+A98-(7+6+54*-32-1)
2384	03988	1-2-(-34*5*(-6-(78-9A)))+B)	-B+A-9+8+(-76-5)*(-4-32*1)
2385	03989	1-2-3*(4-(5-(6+78-9A)))	B+A9-87+65*43+21
2386	03990	-12*(-345+67-(8-9A-B))	-B-A+98-7-(-65*43+21)
2387	03991	-1+2345-67-(-8-(-9+AB))	B+A+(9+8-7-6-5+4^3)^2+1
2388	03992	1*2345-67-(-8+9-AB)	B+A+(9-8)^7+(6-5-4^3)^2+1
2389	03993	-1+2345-67-(8-9-AB)	B*(A9+87+65+43+2+1)
238A	03994	-1+2345+6-78+9+AB	-B-A98-(7+654*3*2*-1)
238B	03995	1+2345+67-(-89+AB)	-B+A98+(-7+65)*(-4-(-32-1))
2390	03996	-1*2*3*(-4-567+8+9A+B)	-BA+9-8-76*(5-43)-2-1
2391	03997	-1+2345+67+8-(9A)-B	BA-9*(8+76)*-5*4-3*-21
2392	03998	1*-2*(-345-67-8-9AB)	-B+A-98-76*(5-43)-21
2393	03999	1+2345-(-6-7*-8)-(-9A+B)	BA9+8-76-54*(-32+1)
2394	04000	1+2345-(67-8-(9A+B))	B-A-98-765*-4-321
2395	04001	1-(-2345-(67-8)-9A)-B	BA-9-8*7-65*-43-2-1
2396	04002	-1+2345+6*(-7+8-9)-A*-B	B+A-9*-8+7-65*-43-21
2397	04003	1+2345+67-8-9+A-B	B-A9+8*(7-6)+(-5-4)*-321

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2398	04004	$-12-3456+78*(9A-B)$	$B+A9-8*(-76+54-321)$
2399	04005	$-1+2345-6+7+8*(9+A-B)$	$BA+987+65*(4-(-3-21))$
239A	04006	$1-2*-34*-5*-6-(7+8)*(-9A+B)$	$-B+A*9*8+7*(654-321)$
239B	04007	$1234+5-(-678+9*A*-B)$	$-BA9-8*(7+6)*(-5-43-(-2+1))$
23A0	04008	$-1+2345+6+78-(9+A)-B$	$BA-9+87-(-65*(43-2)+1)$
23A1	04009	$-1+2345+6-7*8+9+A*B$	$B-A9*(8-7)*(6+5-(4+32))-1$
23A2	04010	$123-4567-89*-A*B$	$-B+A*(-98+7)-(-65*43+21)$
23A3	04011	$1-(-2345-(-67+8-(-9-AB)))$	$B+A+9*8*7+6+(5-4^3)^2-1$
23A4	04012	$-123+4+5*(678-9A)-B$	$B-(-A98-7-6+54*32*-1)$
23A5	04013	$1+2345-6-7+89-A-B$	$-B-A98+76*(54-(3-2)-1)$
23A6	04014	$1-(-2345-6)-(-7*-8-(-9+AB))$	$B+A9+8*-7-65*-43+2+1$
23A7	04015	$-1+2345+67+8+9-A-B$	$-B*(-A+98-765+432)*1$
23A8	04016	$1+2345-6+78-(-9+A)-B$	$BA9-8+7+6*54*3*-2*-1$
23A9	04017	$-1+2345+67+8-(9-A)-B$	$-B+A-9+87+65*43-2-1$
23AA	04018	$-12*(3-45-(-6+7+89+AB))$	$B-A+987-65*(-4+32)*-1$
23AB	04019	$-1+2345-(-67-8+9)-A+B$	$-B+A9-8+7-65*-43-21$
23B0	04020	$-1*-2*(-3-(-456+7*8-9AB))$	$BA-9-8-7+65*43-21$
23B1	04021	$1+2345+67-8+9+A-B$	$BA-9*87+6+54*3*21$
23B2	04022	$-1+234*5+678+9AB$	$-BA-9*-8*7-6*(5-432-1)$
23B3	04023	$-1*23*(45-6-(-7*-8-(-9-AB)))$	$BA+98-7+65*(43-2)-1$
23B4	04024	$1+234*5-(-678-9AB)$	$BA-(-98+7*(65-432-1))$
23B5	04025	$-12+3*(-4+5+67+89A)-B$	$B-(-A98-76+54*(-32+1))$
23B6	04026	$1+2345+67-89+A*B$	$B-A*9-8+(-7+6)*(5+4)*-321$
23B7	04027	$-1-23+45*67-(-8-(-9-AB))$	$BA+9+87+65*(43-2)*1$
23B8	04028	$1+2345+6-(-78-(9-A-B))$	$-B+A9*87+6-5432*1$
23B9	04029	$1-234+56*(7-8*9+AB)$	$B-A98+7+654*3*2-1$
23BA	04030	$1234-5+6*78+9AB$	$B-A98+7+654*3*-2*-1$
23BB	04031	$-1+2345-6-(7-89)+A-B$	$BA9-8+7+6+543*(2+1)$
2400	04032	$-1*-2*(3*4-5+6+78-9)*(A+B)$	$B+A+98-7+65*43-21$
2401	04033	$1+2345-6-7+89+A-B$	$-BA9-8+76*54-3*-2*-1$
2402	04034	$1+2345+6-7-8*-9+A+B$	$-BA-9*-8*(7-(-65+4)+3-21)$
2403	04035	$-1-2*34*-56-789-AB$	$BA9-(-8-7)-(-6-543*(2+1))$
2404	04036	$-1+2345-6-(-78-9)-A+B$	$-BA9-876*-5-4-321$
2405	04037	$-1+2345-(-67-8)+9-A+B$	$B*(-A+9-(87-654)-321)$
2406	04038	$1+2345-(6-78-9+A)+B$	$BA+9-8-7+65*43-21$
2407	04039	$-1+2345+67-(-8+9-A)+B$	$BA+98+7-65*(-43+2)+1$
2408	04040	$-12-(3-45*67)-(-8-9)-AB$	$B+A98-7*-6+54*32-1$
2409	04041	$123+45*(67-8)+9A-B$	$B-(-A9+8)+7-(-65*43+21)$
240A	04042	$-123-45*-67-89+AB$	$B-A9-8*-7*65+4*-32*1$
240B	04043	$-1-(-2345-(6-(7-89-A+B)))$	$BA-(-987-6+54*(-32-1))$
2410	04044	$-1*2*-3*(4+56-7*-89-AB)$	$B-A+(-9-(876+543))*-2-1$
2411	04045	$-1-(-2345-67-(-89+AB))$	$BA9-8-76*(-54-32*-1)$
2412	04046	$1234-56*(78-(-9+AB))$	$BA9-8-76+54*32-1$
2413	04047	$1+2345+67-89+AB$	$BA9-87-(-6-54*32+1)$
2414	04048	$-1-(-2345-6+7)-(-8+9)+A*B$	$B*(-A+9)*(87-654+321)$
2415	04049	$1+2345-6+7+89-A+B$	$BA-98-76+(5+4)*321$
2416	04050	$-1*-2*-3*(-456-(7-89)-AB)$	$-B-(-A-98-7+65*-43-2+1)$
2417	04051	$1-2-34*-56-7-8+9AB$	$BA-98+7*(-6+5*-4+3)*-21$
2418	04052	$1+2-3+4*567-8*(-9A+B)$	$B+A-(9*-8-7+65*-43)+21$
2419	04053	$-12+34*-56*(7-8)+9AB$	$B+A-9*-8*(7-6+54-(-3-2*1))$
241A	04054	$1-(-2345-6)+7-(8-9A+B)$	$-BA-98-765*-4-3-21$
241B	04055	$-1-(2-3-45*67-(8-9-AB))$	$B+A9-8-7-65*-43+2+1$
2420	04056	$-1-(-2345-(-6+78))-9-(-A-B))$	$B+A+9+8*7+(6-5-4^3)^2+1$
2421	04057	$1-23-45*-67-89-A+B$	$B+A9+8-(-7+65*-43+21)$
2422	04058	$-1+2345-6-7+(8-9)*-AB$	$BA98+7*6*(54-321)$
2423	04059	$1+2345-(-6-7-89)+A-B$	$B*(A-9-87+654-321)$
2424	04060	$123+4-56*-7*8+9*(A+B)$	$BA9-8+76+5*(-4+321)$
2425	04061	$1-2+3+(45-6)*-7*-8+9AB$	$B-A+98*(7+6+5*-4)*(-3+2*-1)$
2426	04062	$-1+2345-(-6-7)-8+9A+B$	$BA9+8-76+54*32-1$
2427	04063	$123-45*(-67+8)+9A+B$	$-BA-(9-8*76*5+432*-1)$
2428	04064	$1+2345-6+7-8+9A+B$	$BA9+8*-76+5*432+1$
2429	04065	$-1+2345+6-7+89+A+B$	$B+A-9+8*76*5-4+321$
242A	04066	$1-(2+34*-56+(-7+8)*-9AB)$	$-BA+987+654*3+21$
242B	04067	$1-(-2345-6-(-7+89)-(-A+B))$	$-B+A98+76+54*32*1$
2430	04068	$1*2345-(-6-7)-(-8+9-AB)$	$B+A9+8-(7+65*43*(-2+1))$
2431	04069	$1+2-34*-56+7-8+9AB$	$B-A98-7*(-6-543-21)$
2432	04070	$1-2345+6*(78+9AB)$	$B+A-98+76*(-5+43)+21$
2433	04071	$-1+2345+6-7-8+9+AB$	$-B+A9+8-7+65*43+21$
2434	04072	$12+3+45*67+8-9-AB$	$BA9-(8-7*65)-4*-321$
2435	04073	$1-(-2345-6+7+8-9-AB)$	$-BA-9-8*(76-5-432+1)$
2436	04074	$12*-3*(4-5)*(6+7+89-A-B)$	$BA9-(-8-7*-6*(-5-43))+2-1$
2437	04075	$-12+3456-78*(9A)+B$	$-BA-(98+765*-4+3*2+1)$
2438	04076	$1+2345+6+7-8+9A+B$	$B-(9-8)-(-7-65*43-2)-1$
2439	04077	$-1+2345-(-6+7)*(-8-(9A+B))$	$-B+A987+6*-54*32+1$
243A	04078	$1+2345-(-6+7)-(-8-9A)+B$	$BA9+87-(-6+54)*(-32-1)$
243B	04079	$-1+2345+6+7+89+A+B$	$-BA-(98-765*4-3*(-2+1))$
2440	04080	$1*2*-34*(-56-(78-9A+B))$	$-BA-9-8*(76-5-432)-1$
2441	04081	$1+2345+6+7+89+A+B$	$-BA-(98+765*4*(-3+2))-1$
2442	04082	$-1*(23-45)*(-67+89+AB)$	$-B-A9-(-87-6)-(-5+4)*-321$
2443	04083	$1+2-34*(-5-(67+8))-(-9-A+B))$	$-BA9+8-76*-54+3+21$
2444	04084	$1+23-45*-67-(-8+9)*AB$	$BA-9-8-(-7-65*43)+21$
2445	04085	$-1-(-2345-6)+7-8-(-9-AB)$	$-BA-(98+7)-(-6+54)*-3*21$
2446	04086	$-1+23+45*67-8-9A*-B$	$BA-9-(-8+7)-(-65*-43-21)$
2447	04087	$-1+2345+6-7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+87-(-6-5*(-4+321))$
2448	04088	$12*(345+6-78-9A+B)$	$BA9+8-7*-65-4*-321$
2449	04089	$1+2345+6-(7-8-(9+AB))$	$B+A98+76-54*32*-1$
244A	04090	$-1-2345*(6-7)+8-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A-9-(-8+7-6)-(-5-4)*321$
244B	04091	$-1+2345-6-7*-8-9-A*-B$	$B-(-A+9+8+7+65*(-43-2))-1$
2450	04092	$-1*2*(-3*-4-567-89A+B)$	$B*(-A9+8+76)*(5-4+3)*(-2-1)$
2451	04093	$-123+4-5*(-67+8)*(-9A+B)$	$BA-9*8-76-(-5-4)*321$
2452	04094	$1+2+3+4+5*67+8-9A+B$	$-BA9+8-76*-54+32+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2453	04095	$-1-23-45^*-67+8^*(-9-A+B)$	$-B+A9-87-65^*(-43-2)-1$
2454	04096	$1^*-2^*(3^*-456-78-9-A-B)$	$B-(-A-98)+7-(-65^*43-21)$
2455	04097	$-1+2345-67+89+AB$	$-BA-9^*(-8+7)^*(654-321)$
2456	04098	$-12+3+4-5^*(6+78^*-9-(A-B))$	$B+A987-6^*-54^*32^*-1$
2457	04099	$1+2345-67+89+AB$	$B+A987-6^*-54^*-32+1$
2458	04100	$-1-234^*(-56+7)-89AB$	$BA9-87-6-54^*(-32-1)$
2459	04101	$-1-(-2345+6^*7)-(-8^*9-AB)$	$-BA+9-8+7^*6^*(54+32-1)$
245A	04102	$12-(3+45^*-67)+8^*(9-A-B)$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6-5)^4+3-2+1$
245B	04103	$-1+2345-(-67-89+A+B)$	$-BA+9+8^*-7^*-65-43-21$
2460	04104	$-1-2-3456-7^*(8-9AB)$	$BA+9+8-7-(-65^*43-21)$
2461	04105	$1+23-45^*(-6^*7-8)+9AB$	$BA9+876+(-5+43)^*21$
2462	04106	$-1-2-3+4^*(56+7-8^*-9A+B)$	$-BA-9^*(8-7)^*(-6-5-(4+321))$
2463	04107	$-123+4-5-6^*7^*89-AB$	$B+A9+8+7+65^*43+21$
2464	04108	$-1+2-3456-7^*(-8+9AB)$	$BA9-(8-76)-543^*(-2-1)$
2465	04109	$-1+23-45^*-67-89-A+B$	$-B+A-9+(8-7)^*6+(-5-4)^*-321$
2466	04110	$1+2345+6^*7+89+A+B$	$BA9-8+76^*(-5-4)^*-3-21$
2467	04111	$12+3+45^*67-8^*9-(A+B)$	$BA9-8-76+54^*(32+1)$
2468	04112	$12+3+4+5^*6^*78-9A^*-B$	$B-(-A+9)+87^*(65-4^*3-21)$
2469	04113	$-1234+56^*78+9A-B$	$-B-A+9+8^*-7-6^*(54+32)^*-1$
246A	04114	$1+2345+67-8-(-9-A^*-B)$	$-B+A+9-8+7-6-(5+4)^*-321$
246B	04115	$-1+23-4^*-56^*(7+8)-(-9A-B)$	$BA-98+7+65^*(43+2)+1$
2470	04116	$12^*3^*(-4-(5+6))-(-7-(89-A)))+B)$	$B-A-(98-76^*(5+4+32))-1$
2471	04117	$-12-(-3-45^*67)-8^*-9-AB$	$-B-A9-8-765^*-4+3^*-21$
2472	04118	$-12+3+4^*567-8^*-9A-B$	$BA^*(98+7-(-6-5^*4^*(3+2)^*-1))$
2473	04119	$1-2^*-3-4^*(-56-7-8^*9A-B)$	$-BA-98+765^*4+32-1$
2474	04120	$1234-(-5+67^*-8-9AB)$	$-BA-98+765^*4-32^*-1$
2475	04121	$1234-56-(78+9)^*(-A-B)$	$-BA-98+765^*4+32+1$
2476	04122	$-12-3^*(45-678)+9AB$	$-BA+9^*(876-543)+21$
2477	04123	$-1+2345-6-(-7-8^*9-A^*B)$	$-BA-(-9-8^*7^*(65+4-(3+2^*1)))$
2478	04124	$-1+2345-(-67+89^*(A-B))$	$-BA-9^*(87-(6+5^*43))^*(2+1)$
2479	04125	$-1+2345+67+89-A+B$	$-B^*(-A9+8+76-5+43)^*-21$
247A	04126	$1+2345+67-89^*(A-B)$	$-B+A9-8^*-7-65^*-43+21$
247B	04127	$-1+2345-6+78-(-9+A^*-B)$	$BA9+8-(76-54^*(32+1))$
2480	04128	$-1^*-2^*(3-4)^*(-5-67^*8-9AB)$	$-B+A9+8+7^*6+5^*(432-1)$
2481	04129	$1+2345-6-(-78+9^*-A)+B$	$B-A-9^*8-7^*6^*5^*4^*(-3+2^*-1)$
2482	04130	$1+2345+67-(-8+9-A^*B)$	$-BA+9+8^*7^*65-(43-2^*1)$
2483	04131	$-1^*(-2345-67+8-9-A^*B)$	$BA9+8-7^*-6+54^*(32-1)$
2484	04132	$1+2345-6-(7+8^*-9)+AB$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4+3-2-1$
2485	04133	$-1-(-2345+6-(78+9A)+B)$	$-BA-9^*(8-76+54-321)$
2486	04134	$1^*-2^*(-3^*456+7-8-(9+AB))$	$-BA-9^*-8^*7-65^*(-43+2)-1$
2487	04135	$1+2345+67-8-9+AB$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4+3-2+1$
2488	04136	$1+2345+67+8+9A-B$	$-BA9-8^*(-7-6)^*(5+43)+21$
2489	04137	$-12-3+4^*(567-8)-9^*-A^*B$	$BA9-(8+7-6+54^*-32-1)$
248A	04138	$-123-(-4-5)-(6^*7^*-89+A^*B)$	$-BA9-8+7-65^*(-43-21)$
248B	04139	$1^*2-3+4^*(567-(-89-AB))$	$-BA+9-8^*(-7-(6+54+321))$
2490	04140	$1^*2^*-3^*(-456+78-(9+AB))$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6-5-43^*21$
2491	04141	$1+2345-(-6-78)+9^*A+B$	$BA+98+765^*4-321$
2492	04142	$1+2345+67-8-9A-B$	$-BA-9-8-765^*-4-32-1$
2493	04143	$-12-3^*(4-56-78)^*9A-B$	$-BA-9-8+765^*4-32^*1$
2494	04144	$-1-2-3+4+5^*-6^*-78+9AB$	$-B+A9-(876+543)^*2^*-1$
2495	04145	$-1+2345+67+89+A+B$	$B+A9+87-65^*-43-21$
2496	04146	$-1-2+3+4^*(5+6+78-9A)-B$	$-B+A9+87-65^*-43+2^*-1$
2497	04147	$1+2345+6+78+9A-B$	$-B+A9+87+65^*43-2+1$
2498	04148	$-1+2345-6+78-9+AB$	$B+A9-8^*-7-65^*-43+21$
2499	04149	$1+2-3^*(-45-(-6-(78-9AB)))$	$BA9-(8-7)-(-6-(54^*32-1))$
249A	04150	$-12+3+45^*67+89-AB$	$-B-A9^*8^*(-7-6)-5432-1$
249B	04151	$-1234+5^*678+9AB$	$B-A^*(9-(-8-76)-54-321)$
24A0	04152	$1+2^*(-3+4+567+89A)+B$	$B-(-A+9^*(8-76)^*5)-(-4-321)$
24A1	04153	$-1-(-2+3)-4^*(5+6)^*-78-9A+B)$	$-BA-9-8-765^*-4-32-1$
24A2	04154	$-1+2345+6-7-(-89-A^*B)$	$BA9-87^*-6-5-4^*-321$
24A3	04155	$-1-(-2345+6)+78-(-9A-B)$	$BA9+8+7-6-54^*-32+1$
24A4	04156	$-1-(-2345-67-8-9A-B)$	$-BA-(9-876)+5^*(432-1)$
24A5	04157	$-123+4^*(5+6+78-9^*-A^*B)$	$-BA-98-765^*-4-3^*-21$
24A6	04158	$12^*(34+56-7)^*(-8+(-9A+A)^*B)$	$B^*(-A-9-(87+(-65-43)^*-2))^*-1$
24A7	04159	$1-2^*-3^*(-456-78+9AB)$	$BA+987+65^*(-4+32)^*1$
24A8	04160	$-1-(-2+3+4^*-56)-(-78-9AB)$	$-BA-9+876-5^*-432-1$
24A9	04161	$1234+567+8-9A^*-B$	$-BA-(9+8)-76^*(5-43+2^*-1)$
24AA	04162	$1+2345+6+78-9+AB$	$BA+9^*-87^*-6-543^*2^*1$
24AB	04163	$1-(-2-3)-(-45^*67-89)-AB$	$-B-A+987+654^*3+2-1$
24B0	04164	$1^*2345-6-7+89+AB$	$-B-A+987+654^*3+2^*1$
24B1	04165	$1-23-45^*-67-8-9A+B$	$BA-9-(-87+65^*-43)-2^*-1$
24B2	04166	$1-2+3^*4^*-567-89^*-AB$	$-B-A-98+765^*4-32+1$
24B3	04167	$-1-(-2+3)-(-45^*67+8-(-9A)+B)$	$BA9+8-(-7-6)-(-54^*32-1)$
24B4	04168	$1+2345-6+78-(-9-AB)$	$-B+A-987+654^*3^*2^*1$
24B5	04169	$1-(-2345-6-(78+9A)+B)$	$-BA-9+8-(-765^*4-(-3-21))$
24B6	04170	$-1+2345-6^*(-7-8)+9+AB$	$B+A9-(-87+65^*43^*(-2+1))$
24B7	04171	$123-(-4+5)-(-6^*-7^*(-89+A)-B)$	$-B-A9+8^*-7^*-65-(-4+3)-2^*1$
24B8	04172	$12-3-45^*-67+89-AB$	$B-(-A9-(87+65^*43))-2^*-1$
24B9	04173	$12+3+4^*56+78+9AB$	$-B-A9+876+5^*432+1$
24BA	04174	$1-2+3^*-4+5^*-6^*-78+9AB$	$BA9+87-6^*(54-321)$
24BB	04175	$-1+2345+6-(7-89-AB)$	$-BA-(98+7+6^*-5^*4^*(32-1))$
2500	04176	$-1-2^*3-4-5^*6^*-78+9AB$	$BA+98-7-65^*-43-2^*1$
2501	04177	$1+2345+6-7+89+AB$	$-BA+9-8-765^*-4+3-21$
2502	04178	$-1-(-2345-6-78-(9+AB))$	$B-A98+76^*54-32+1$
2503	04179	$-1-(-2345-6+7)-8^*(-9-A-B)$	$-BA+9+876+5^*432^*1$
2504	04180	$-12+3+4+5^*6^*78+9AB$	$-BA+9+876+5^*432+1$
2505	04181	$1-(-2345+6+(-7-8)^*9-A^*B)$	$BA+98-(-7-65^*43)-(-2-1)$
2506	04182	$1^*(-2-3-4-(-56-7)))(8^*-9A+B)$	$BA-(-9-87-65^*43-2+1)$
2507	04183	$1-23-4^*(56-789)-(-A-B)$	$-BA-9-8-765^*-4+3-2+1$
2508	04184	$-1+2^*(3^*4)+5+6+7+8^*9A-B$	$-B-A98-76^*-54+3^*(-2-1)$
2509	04185	$-1-(-2-(-3-45^*-67)-8+9A-B)$	$BA9-87^*(65-43^*2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
250A	04186	$-12*(3-4-56-(78+9+AB))$	$-B+A-98-765^*-4-(32-1)$
250B	04187	$1-2-(3-4+5^*6^*-78)+9AB$	$-BA-9-8^*7^*-65-(-43+21)$
2510	04188	$1^*23+45^*67+89-AB$	$BA9-(8+7)-(6-54^*(32+1))$
2511	04189	$-1+2345-(-6-7-89)+AB$	$-B+A^*(9+87-65)^*4^*3^*(2-1)$
2512	04190	$1-23^*(45-67)^*8-9AB$	$BA9+87+6-54^*(-32+1)$
2513	04191	$1-(-2345-6-7)-(-89-AB)$	$BA+9^*8^*76+54^*-32+1$
2514	04192	$-1^*(23+4+56+7+8^*-9)^*-AB$	$-B+A9^*8-7^*(-6+5)^*(-4+321)$
2515	04193	$12-3-45^*-67+89-A^*B$	$B-A9+876+5^*432-1$
2516	04194	$-12-345^*-6+(7-8)^*9A^*-B$	$-B+A98+7^*6^*54-32-1$
2517	04195	$-1-2-345^*-6+7+89A+B$	$BA9-(-8-7^*6)-54^*32^*-1$
2518	04196	$-12-3+45^*67-89+AB$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-65+4-321)$
2519	04197	$-1-2+(34-5-(6+7-8))^*(9+AB)$	$-BA9-876^*-5-4^*3^*21$
251A	04198	$1234-56-7+89^*(A+B)$	$-BA-9^*8^*7^*6-(5-4321)$
251B	04199	$1-2^*-3+4^*(-56+789-A+B)$	$-B-A98-76^*-54+3^*2^*1$
2520	04200	$-1^*2^*(-34+5)^*(-6-(7+8^*-9)-(A-B))$	$-B-A-98-765^*-4+3^*(-2+1)$
2521	04201	$1+2+345^*6+7+89A+B$	$B-A^*(-9+8-(76^*5-4-3-21))$
2522	04202	$12-3+4+5^*6^*78+9AB$	$-B^*(A9-(-87-6+5)-432-1)$
2523	04203	$-1+2^*(3^*4)-5+6^*7+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+987-654^*-3-2+1$
2524	04204	$12-(-34-5^*-67^*-8-9^*-A^*-B)$	$BA+9+8^*-76^*-5-4+321$
2525	04205	$-12-3456-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B-A-98+76^*(-5+43+2^*1)$
2526	04206	$-1+2^*(34+567+89A)-B$	$BA+9-87-65^*(-43-2-1)$
2527	04207	$12-345^*-6-7-8+9A^*B$	$-B+A+987-654^*-3+21$
2528	04208	$1-234^*5^*6-(7+89A)^*-B$	$-BA+9^*8^*-7^*6+5+4321$
2529	04209	$12-3^*(-45-67-89A)-B$	$-B-A9+8+765^*4^*(3-2)+1$
252A	04210	$1+23-45^*-67-(-89+A^*B)$	$-B-A-9-8^*(76-5-(432+1))$
252B	04211	$-1+23+45^*67-(-8+9)-(-A+B)$	$-B+A98-(-7^*-6^*-54-3)-21$
2530	04212	$1^*-23^*(-4-(-5-67)-(-89+AB))$	$-B-(A-9)-(-87^*(-6+5+4+32)-1)$
2531	04213	$1+2345+(-67+89)^*A+B$	$-B+A-9^*(-876+543)-21$
2532	04214	$1234-5-6^*7+89^*(A+B)$	$-BA-9+8^*7^*(-6+5^*-4)^*-3-2-1$
2533	04215	$-1+2+3-4+5^*(-6-(78^*-9-A-B))$	$B-A9-(8+765^*4)-(-3+2^*1)$
2534	04216	$-1^*(-23+45^*-67+8-9+A-B)$	$-B+A+9+8-7^*-6^*5^*4^*(3+2)^*1$
2535	04217	$1-2^*(-3-4^*-5^*(-6-7))^*8+9+A-B$	$BA+98+7-65^*-43+21$
2536	04218	$1-(-2-(-3456-7^*(-8-9AB)))$	$-BA-(9+8)-765^*-4-(-32+1)$
2537	04219	$-1+2^*-34-5^*(6-78)^*(9-A+B)$	$B-A9-87-6^*-5^*4^*(32-1)$
2538	04220	$1-(-23+4^*(-56-(789-AB)))$	$-BA+9-8^*(-7+65-432)+1$
2539	04221	$123-45^*-67-(8+9A+B)$	$-BA+9+8+765^*4-3^*-2^*1$
253A	04222	$1-(-2345-6)-(-7-8)^*(9+A)-B$	$-B+A-(-9+8^*76^*-5-432^*1)$
253B	04223	$-1^*(2/-3+4)^*-5-6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-98-(-765^*4-3+21)$
2540	04224	$1-2345+67^*89-AB$	$B-A^*-98-7+6^*-5^*43^*-2^*1$
2541	04225	$1^*-2+34+5^*-6^*-78+9AB$	$BA9+876-5+43^*21$
2542	04226	$1234+5^*-67^*-8-9^*A^*B$	$BA-98+7^*6^*-5^*-4^*(3-2^*-1)$
2543	04227	$-1234-5+6^*(7-8+9)^*AB$	$B+A98+7^*6^*54-(3+21)$
2544	04228	$-12+3-(-4-5)^*(-678+9AB)$	$BA+9^*87-(65+4)^*(-32-1)$
2545	04229	$1+2-34^*(-56-7)+8-9A^*-B$	$B+A-(-987-654^*3-21)$
2546	04230	$-12-3-(45+6^*7^*-89-A^*-B)$	$-B-(A98+76^*-54)+32-1$
2547	04231	$-12-345^*-6-(78-9AB)$	$-B-A9-8+765^*4+32+1$
2548	04232	$1234+56+(7+8)^*(9+AB)$	$-B-A98+76^*54-(-32-1)$
2549	04233	$123+4-5^*6^*-78+9A^*B$	$B+A98+7^*6^*54-(-3+21)$
254A	04234	$-1+2345-(-67-89-A^*B)$	$B+A9+/-8^*(-7+6+5^*4)^*-3^*2+1$
254B	04235	$1^*2345+67+89+A^*B$	$BA9+876+5+43^*21$
2550	04236	$1234-5+6^*-7+(-8-9)^*-AB$	$-B-(A9-8)-765^*-4-(-3-21)$
2551	04237	$12+3+4^*5^*(67-(8-9-AB))$	$-BA-(-9+8)-(-765^*4-32^*1)$
2552	04238	$-123-456+7^*8^*9^*A+B$	$-B+A-9^*(-8+7)^*(654-321)$
2553	04239	$-1^*23^*(45-67+(8-9)^*AB)$	$B+A-(98+765^*4)-3^*2^*1$
2554	04240	$-1^*(-23-45)^*(-67-8+9+AB)$	$BA-(9-87+65^*(-43-2+1))$
2555	04241	$-12-3-456^*-7-89-AB$	$B+A^*-98^*(-7+6)+5^*-432^*-1$
2556	04242	$-1-2-345^*-6-78+9AB$	$BA9+8-(-76+54^*-32)-1$
2557	04243	$123-45^*-67-8-9A+B$	$B-A9-(-8^*7^*65-43)-2^*1$
2558	04244	$1-2-345^*-6-78+9AB$	$B+A-9+8+(7^*6+5^*4+3)^*2-1$
2559	04245	$12-345-6^*(7+8-9)^*-AB$	$-B-A9+8-765^*-4+32-1$
255A	04246	$-1+2-345^*-6-78+9AB$	$B^*(A9-8-7+65-4+321)$
255B	04247	$123-4-5^*(-678+9+AB)$	$-B+A9-(8-76^*(-5+43)+21)$
2560	04248	$-12-3+4^*(-5+678+9A)-B$	$-B-A9-8^*-7^*65+43+21$
2561	04249	$1-2-3^*45+6^*-7^*-89+A-B$	$-BA-(-9+876^*-5+4^*321)$
2562	04250	$1+2-(-3+4^*5+6^*7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA9-8+7^*(654-3^*21)$
2563	04251	$-1-234^*5+6^*(789-AB)$	$B-A9-8-765^*-4+32-1$
2564	04252	$-123-45^*-67+89+AB$	$B-A98-76^*-54+32-1$
2565	04253	$1+2-34^*-5^*6^*7+89^*A^*-B$	$BA9+87+6-54^*-32-1$
2566	04254	$1-23+4^*(56+7^*-8)^*(9A-B)$	$BA9-(-87-6)-54^*32^*-1$
2567	04255	$-1+2345+67+89+AB$	$BA9+87+6-54^*-32+1$
2568	04256	$-1^*(-2345-67-89-AB)$	$BA9+8^*76-5+4^*321$
2569	04257	$12-3+45^*67-8^*9+AB$	$-BA+98-7^*6^*(-54-32)-1$
256A	04258	$1+2-3+456^*7-89-AB$	$B-A9+8+765^*4+3+21$
256B	04259	$12-345^*-6-78+9AB$	$-B+A^*-9-8^*(-7-65-4-321)$
2570	04260	$12-3-(45+6)^*-78-9^*AB$	$-B+A-(98+765^*-4-32+1)$
2571	04261	$1-(-2345-67-8^*(9+A+B))$	$B+A+9^*-8+7^*(6-(5-432)+1)$
2572	04262	$(-1+2)^*-3+(-4-5)^*-6^*(7+8^*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A-9+8^*(76-5+432^*-1))$
2573	04263	$-12+3-45^*-67+8-(-9^*A+B)$	$B-(A+98-765^*4-32^*1)$
2574	04264	$1^*-234^*(5-6-7+89+A^*B)$	$-B-A-9-8-765^*-4+32^*-1$
2575	04265	$123+45^*67+8^*-9-A-B$	$-B+A-9^*(8^*(-7+6)-5-4-321)$
2576	04266	$-1^*-23^*(-45+67-(8-9)+AB)$	$B+A+9^*8^*7+6^*5^*4-3^*2^*1$
2577	04267	$-12+345^*6+7^*-8+9AB$	$-B+A+98^*7^*-6+5^*4^*321$
2578	04268	$-1-23-45^*-67+8-(-9^*A-B)$	$B-(A9-8)-(-765^*4-32^*1)$
2579	04269	$1+2345+6^*-7^*-8-9^*(A+B)$	$B-A9^*(-8-(7-(-6-5)+4)-3)+2-1$
257A	04270	$12^*(-34+5^*(-67+8+9+AB))$	$-BA9+87^*(-6+54)+3^*(2+1)$
257B	04271	$1-(-2-3+4-56^*(-7+8^*9))-(-A-B))$	$-B-(-A98+7^*6^*-54)-32^*-1$
2580	04272	$-1+23-45^*-67-8^*9+AB$	$B+A+9^*8^*7+6^*5^*4-3/(2-1)$
2581	04273	$-1+2^*3-4^*(5+6-(-7+89+A))^*B$	$-BA+9-8^*-7-(6-54)^*-3^*-21$
2582	04274	$1234+567-8+9AB$	$B+A^*-9+8+765^*4+3+2^*1$
2583	04275	$-12-3^*(-4+56+78)^*-9+AB$	$B+A^*-9-8-765^*-4-(3-21)$
2584	04276	$1-2345-67^*(-89-A+B)$	$B+A98+7^*(-6-54+321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2585	04277	$123-4-5*(6+78*-9)*(-A+B)$	$-B-A-(9-876+5*(-432+1))$
2586	04278	$-1*2*(-3-(4-56)+7+89*(-A-B))$	$-B-A98-7+65*(43+21)$
2587	04279	$-12+3*45*(-6+7-89+AB)$	$B*(-A+98+76-(54*-3-2)-1)$
2588	04280	$1*2+3-4+5*(6+78)*9-AB$	$-B-(-A-987*6)-(5+4)*321$
2589	04281	$-1*(23-4-(-56+78))*9AB$	$BA+9*(8+7)-65*(-43-(2-1))$
258A	04282	$-1+2345-678-9A*-B$	$B-A9*8-76*-54-321$
258B	04283	$-1-2-3*4-5-(-6*-7*-89+AB)$	$-B-A98-76*(-54-3-2*-1)$
2590	04284	$1-(-2345+678+9A*-B)$	$-BA+98+(-76+5)*-43-21$
2591	04285	$-1-23+456*7+8-9*(A+B)$	$-B+A+9-(8+7*6*(-54-32))+1$
2592	04286	$-12-345*-6+78-9A*-B$	$B+A*9*-8*-7+6-543*(2-1)$
2593	04287	$12+3-4-5-(-6*7*89+AB)$	$B-A*9-(-8-76-5*4)*(32-1)$
2594	04288	$1*2^(3*4)+5*6*7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A-9-8-7*(-6-(-5+432))+1$
2595	04289	$-1-234*(-5-6)-(-7*-8-9A)*B$	$BA+987-6*(-5+4-321)$
2596	04290	$1234-(-567-8-9AB)$	$-B*-A*(9+8+7*-6+54-(3-2)+1)$
2597	04291	$12+3-45*-67+8-9*-A-B$	$BA9-8+76-54*(-32-1)$
2598	04292	$-1+23*4+5*(678-9A*-B)$	$-B-(A98-7-65*(43+21))$
2599	04293	$-12+3456-(78+9AB)$	$-B+A*9-8*-7*6*5+432*1$
259A	04294	$-1+23*4-5*6*-78+9AB$	$B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4*(3+2)+1$
259B	04295	$1234-5+(6-78-9A)*-B$	$BA+9*(8+7)*-6*-5+43*2+1$
25A0	04296	$-123-45-(-6*7*89+A*-B)$	$-BA-98*7-(6+54)*-3*21$
25A1	04297	$12-3-(45*-67+8)+9A-B$	$-B+A-9+876-5*(-432+1)$
25A2	04298	$-123+45+6*-78*(-9-A+B)$	$-BA+9*8+765*4+3+21$
25A3	04299	$1-2*3^4-56-(789-AB)$	$-B-A+9*(8-(-765+432)+1)$
25A4	04300	$123-4*-567-8*-9A-B$	$BA+987+654*3-21$
25A5	04301	$1234+5+6+7+(-8-9)*-AB$	$-B+A9-(-87-65*(43+2))-1$
25A6	04302	$123-4+5*(678-9A-B)$	$B-A9+8*-7-6*(-543+21)$
25A7	04303	$12+3-(-45*67+8)-(-9A+B)$	$BA+9-8*(76+5-432)*1$
25A8	04304	$-1-2+3456-78-9AB$	$BA-9*87*-6+(5+43)*-21$
25A9	04305	$-1+23-456*-7-89-A*B$	$BA9-87-65*(4-32-1)$
25AA	04306	$1-2-(-3456+78+9AB)$	$B-A*9*8*(-7+6-5)*(-4-3)-21$
25AB	04307	$-1-2+34+5*(-67-8*-9A-B)$	$BA+9+8*7*65-4*(32+1)$
25B0	04308	$-1+2-(-3456+78+9AB)$	$-BA+98+765*4-3*-2*-1$
25B1	04309	$1+2345-(-6*(78-9)+AB)$	$-B-A+98-7*(6+5-432+1)$
25B2	04310	$1+2+3456-78-9AB$	$BA9-8*-7-65*(4-32+1)$
25B3	04311	$-123+45*(67+8)-(-9A+B)$	$-B-A-(9-8-765*4)-(-3*-2+1)$
25B4	04312	$-1*(-2-(345-(6+7)+8))-9*-A)*B$	$B*(A9+8-(-76+5+432))*-1$
25B5	04313	$12-3-45*-67+8+9A-B$	$B+A+9-8-7*(6-5+4*3*2)^1$
25B6	04314	$12+345*6+78-9A*-B$	$-B-A9-(-8-765*4-3)-21$
25B7	04315	$1234+5-(-678-9A*B)$	$BA9-8+76*(-5-4+32)*1$
25B8	04316	$-1-234-56*-78-9AB$	$-BA+987-6-5*(-432+1)$
25B9	04317	$1-23-(-4-5*67*8)+9*AB$	$-B+A+9+8-765*-4-32-1$
25BA	04318	$1-234-56*-78-9AB$	$B+A+9+8*-7*-65+4-(3+21)$
25BB	04319	$1-(2-3)-(-45*67-8+9)+AB$	$B-(A-9-8)-(-765*4-(-32-1))$
2600	04320	$-1*(-23+45*-67-89+A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9-876)-5*-432*1$
2601	04321	$12+3456-78-9AB$	$-BA+987-6-5*432*-1$
2602	04322	$-123-456*-7+8-9*(-A+B)$	$B-(A-9)-(-876+5*-432*1)$
2603	04323	$-1+2+345*6-7-8+9AB$	$B+A-9*(-8-765-(-432-1))$
2604	04324	$-12+345*6-(7-(8+9AB))$	$B+A-9-(-876+5*432*-1)$
2605	04325	$-1234-567*8*(9-A)-B$	$B+A9+87+65*(43+2)+1$
2606	04326	$-1234-567*-8-(9-A+B)$	$-BA+987-6+5*(432+1)$
2607	04327	$1-2+3+4*(-5+6+789)-AB$	$BA+987-654*-3+2*1$
2608	04328	$1*-2*(-3-(456+78+9AB))$	$BA-(-987-654*3-(2+1))$
2609	04329	$-12+3456+7*-8-9AB$	$BA-98+765*4-(32-1)$
260A	04330	$12+3+45*67-(-89-A-B)$	$-B-A-98*7*-6-54-321$
260B	04331	$-123-4*-567+8+9A*B$	$-BA+98+7-(-6+54)*3*-21$
2610	04332	$-1-2+34-5-6*7*-89+A*-B$	$B+A*9*(87+6-54+3)+2-1$
2611	04333	$-123-4*(5+67+(-8+9A)*-B)$	$-B-(-A98-7+654*-3)-(2+1)$
2612	04334	$1-2+34-5+6*7*89+A*-B$	$BA+987*(-6-(-5-4))-3+2*-1$
2613	04335	$1234+56*7*8-9AB$	$-B+A+9-8-(765*4+3)-2*1$
2614	04336	$-1+2345+(-67-89-A)*-B$	$B-(A-9-8+765*-4)-(-3+21)$
2615	04337	$12+3*(4+56-7*8+9AB)$	$-BA9-8+(-7-6)*(-5-4-321)$
2616	04338	$-1+2-345*-6-(7-8)*9AB$	$-B+A98+7*(6-54+321)$
2617	04339	$-1/-2*(3+(4-5+6)^7-8)/9+A-B$	$B+A*9+8-76*(5-43-2+1)$
2618	04340	$-1+2+34*(56+7)-8+9AB$	$B-A*(-987+654+32)-1$
2619	04341	$-1*(2-3456-7*-8+9AB)$	$B+A+9+876+5*432-1$
261A	04342	$-1+23+4*567-8*(-9-AB)$	$BA9-87*-6*5-4-321$
261B	04343	$1+2-3+4-5*-6*7*8+9*AB$	$-B-A-9-87-6*(-543+21)$
2620	04344	$-1234+567*8+9A-B$	$B+A-9*87-(-6-54)*3*21$
2621	04345	$-1234-567*-8-9*(A-B)$	$B*(A98-765-43-21)$
2622	04346	$1-(-2-3456)-7*8-9AB$	$B-A-9-8-765*-4-3+21$
2623	04347	$-12-3+456*7-8+9-AB$	$BA-9-(-8*76*5-432*1)$
2624	04348	$-1-(-2+3*(-45-6-78-9A*B))$	$-B-(A-9*(-8-76)*-5+4)-32+1$
2625	04349	$-1+2*-3*(4-5-6+78*-9-A*-B)$	$B+A98+7-(-654+3)*(2+1)$
2626	04350	$-1+23-(-45*67-8-9A-B)$	$-BA9-(-8-76*(54+3)-21)$
2627	04351	$-12-3-456*-7-(89+A)-B$	$-BA-(-98-765*4)-(-32+1)$
2628	04352	$-1+2345-6*-78-(9+AB)$	$BA9-87-6*(5-4)*-321$
2629	04353	$-1-2345+67*-89*(A-B)$	$-BA-(-98+765*-4)+32+1$
262A	04354	$123-4-5*-6*78+9AB$	$B-(A+98)-(-7-6*(543-21))$
262B	04355	$-1-23-4*-567+8-9*-AB$	$-B-A*98+(7-654)*(-3-2-1)$
2630	04356	$-1*2*(34-567+8-9AB)$	$B*(A+9-8+76-5-4*3*-21)$
2631	04357	$1+2*(-3+4-56-(7+8)-9A)*-B$	$BA9+87-65*(4-32+1)$
2632	04358	$1*-2+3-45-6*7*-89*(-A+B)$	$-B-A9-87-6*-543-21$
2633	04359	$-1*(-2+3-4)*(-56-(-78-9AB))$	$B+A98-(-7-654*3)-(-2+1)$
2634	04360	$1*-2*(-34-5-678-9*AB)$	$-BA-9-87-6*(543-2)*-1$
2635	04361	$-12+345*(-6+7+8)+9-A+B$	$-B+A+98*-7*-6+5*43*-2*1$
2636	04362	$123-(-4-5*-6*-78)+9AB$	$B+A+9-8+765*4-3+2+1$
2637	04363	$1+23-45*-67+8+9+AB$	$BA9+876+54*(-3+21)$
2638	04364	$-1-2*-3-456*-7-8-(9A+B)$	$BA+9+8*76*5+432-1$
2639	04365	$123-4*-567+8+9A*B$	$B+A-(-9+8-765)*4-(-3+2+1)$
263A	04366	$1+2*3^4(-4+5+6)-7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A*(-9-87)+(-65+4)*3*-21$
263B	04367	$1234+5+67-(-8-9)*AB$	$-BA9-8*(-76-5)*4*(3-2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2640	04368	$1+2+3-456^*-7+8-9-AB$	$-B-A-98+(76-5)^*(43+2)^*1$
2641	04369	$-1+23+4^*(567-8)+9^*AB$	$B-(-A98-(-7-654^*-3)-21)$
2642	04370	$-12+3456-(7+8+9AB)$	$-B-A-(-9+876^*-5-4^*-321)$
2643	04371	$-123-(4-5-6^*-7^*-89-AB)$	$BA-98+765^*4-(-3-2)^*1$
2644	04372	$1+2345+6^*78+9-AB$	$-BA-(9+87-6^*-543^*(-2+1))$
2645	04373	$1+2-(-345+678)^*-9+AB$	$-B-A98-76^*(-54-(3-2+1))$
2646	04374	$123-45^*-67-(-8-(9+A))-B$	$BA+9-87^*(6-(-5+43+2-1))$
2647	04375	$1+234+5^*(-67-8)^*-9+AB$	$-B-A9^*8+7^*(6+543-2-1)$
2648	04376	$123+45^*67+8+9-(A-B)$	$B-A9^*8-76^*-5^*-4^*-3-2-1$
2649	04377	$1+23+45^*(-6+78)-(-9+A)^*B$	$-B-A+98+(7+65)^*43+2^*-1$
264A	04378	$-1+2345+6^*-78-9^*-A^*B$	$-BA-9-87+6^*(543+2-1)$
264B	04379	$12+3-456^*-7+8-9-AB$	$B-A-9+8-(-765^*4-32)+1$
2650	04380	$1-(-2345-6^*-78)-9^*-A^*B$	$-B-(-A+98^*7^*6)-(-5432+1)$
2651	04381	$-1-2+3456-7-8-9AB$	$-BA-98^*(-7-6-54+32)-1$
2652	04382	$-12^*(3+45^*-6+7+89+A^*-B)$	$B+A-9-8-765^*-4+32^*1$
2653	04383	$-1+23+456^*7-8-9A-B$	$B+A98-(-7-654^*3-21)$
2654	04384	$-12+3456+7-8-9AB$	$B-A^*(-98-76)-543^*(-2-1)$
2655	04385	$-1+2345+6^*78-(9A-B)$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6-5+4^3)^2-1$
2656	04386	$-12+3456-7+8-9AB$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6-5+4^3)^2/1$
2657	04387	$1+2+3456-(7+8)-9AB$	$B+A-(-98+(76-5)^*(-43-(-2+1)))$
2658	04388	$-1^*-2^*(-34+567-(-8-9AB))$	$BA-98-765^*-4-3+21$
2659	04389	$1+2^*(-34+567-(-8-9AB))$	$-B^*(A+9)^*(8+7-(-6+54+3-21))$
265A	04390	$12+3+456^*7+8-9A-B$	$BA-9^*(-876-(-543+2-1))$
265B	04391	$-12+3-45^*-67+89-A^*-B$	$-BA-(-9+87)+6^*543-(-2+1)$
2660	04392	$-1-23+45-6^*(7+8-9)^*-AB$	$BA9-87+654^*3-2^*1$
2661	04393	$-1+23-456^*-7-(8+9-A^*-B)$	$BA9-8+7^*6^*-54^*(-3+2)^*1$
2662	04394	$1+2-3^*4^*-5^*(6-7+8+9)+AB$	$BA9-87-654^*-3^*(2-1)$
2663	04395	$-1-2+3456-(-7+8+9AB)$	$-B-A-9-(-8+7+6-54)^*-3^*-21$
2664	04396	$12+3-(-456^*7-(-8-9A+B))$	$BA-(9-8^*7^*65+43)-2^*-1$
2665	04397	$1-2-(-3456-7)-(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A-9-8-(-765^*4-3^*21)$
2666	04398	$12+34^*-5^*-67+8^*-9AB$	$B-(-A9+8^*-7^*65)-43-(2+1)$
2667	04399	$1-2+3456-7-(-8+9AB)$	$BA9-8-7-(-65+4)^*(32-1)$
2668	04400	$-12+3456+7+8-9AB$	$-B-A-(-98+7^*(-6+5+432)^*1)$
2669	04401	$1^*-23^*(4-(-5+67)-(-8-9)+A^*-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5^*4^*3)^2^*1$
266A	04402	$1-(-2-3456+(7-8)^*-9AB)$	$-BA^*(-9-(8+7+6)-5-(4+3+2+1))$
266B	04403	$1+2+3456-(7-8+9AB)$	$B-(-A+98^*-7^*-6)+5432^*1$
2670	04404	$1^*2+(3+4+5^*6)^*7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA-98-765^*-4-32^*-1$
2671	04405	$-1+2+3+456^*7+8^*-9-(A+B)$	$-B-(A9+8^*7-6^*543)-21$
2672	04406	$1-2-3+456^*7-(89-A-B)$	$BA-9+8+765^*4+3^*-21$
2673	04407	$12+3-456^*-7-89-A+B$	$B-A9-87+6^*543+2^*1$
2674	04408	$1^*-2^*(-3+45-678+9A^*-B)$	$BA-98+7^*(6+5-(-432-1))$
2675	04409	$1-23+456^*7-8^*-9-AB$	$-BA9-(876+5-4321)$
2676	04410	$-12^*3^*(4-5)^*(67-89+AB)$	$-B-A987-65^*4^*-3^*21$
2677	04411	$-1+2345-678+9AB$	$-B-A^*-9-8-765^*-4+3-2-1$
2678	04412	$12+3456+7-8-9AB$	$BA-9+87^*6^*-5+4321$
2679	04413	$1-(-2345+678-9AB)$	$-B-A+98+765^*4+3-21$
267A	04414	$12+3456-(7-(-8-9AB))$	$B-A9-87^*(-6-5)^*4+3-(2+1)$
267B	04415	$-12-345^*-6+78+9AB$	$B+A+(9+8-7-6+5+4)^3^*2^*1$
2680	04416	$-1^*(2-3+4+5)^*-6^*(-7-(-8-(9A-B)))$	$-B+A9+8+7^*(-6+5+432)-1$
2681	04417	$-1-2-3+45^*67+89+AB$	$-B-(-A-(98-765^*-4+32^*-1))$
2682	04418	$1-(23+4^*(-5+6-789-A+B))$	$B-A+98+765^*4-32-1$
2683	04419	$1+2345+6^*(78-9)-(A+B)$	$B+A9-87^*6^*5+4321$
2684	04420	$-1+2345+6^*(78+9-A-B)$	$-B-(-A9-8^*7^*65+4)-(-3+2+1)$
2685	04421	$-1+2^*(-3-4-(-567+8)+9AB)$	$BA9+8+76^*5^*(4-(-3+2)+1)$
2686	04422	$-12+3456-(78-9A^*-B)$	$B^*(-A+98+7+6^*-5+43)^*(2+1)$
2687	04423	$-12-3-4^*5^*-6^*(-78+9A+B)$	$BA-9-8-7^*(6-5-432-1)$
2688	04424	$(-1+2-(3^4-5))^*(6+7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-BA-9^*8^*7^*-6+543^*-2^*-1$
2689	04425	$1^*(-2-3)^*(-456-7-(89+AB))$	$-B+A+98-(-76+5)^*43-21$
268A	04426	$-1-2-345^*-6+78+9AB$	$-BA9-876^*-5+4+3^*-21$
268B	04427	$1-23-45^*-6^*7+(8+9)^*AB$	$B-A9-8^*-7^*(65-4)+321$
2690	04428	$12+3456-(-7-8)-9AB$	$B+A+98-7^*(-6+5)^*(432-1)$
2691	04429	$-1-23-45^*(6-78)-(-9-A^*-B)$	$B-(-A-98)-(-7^*(-6+5+432)-1)$
2692	04430	$-1^*(2+3)^*(-45-6-78^*9-(A-B))$	$B-(A9+87)-(-6^*543-21)$
2693	04431	$-12-(-3-45-6^*-7^*-89-(-A-B))$	$-B-(A-98+765^*-4)-(-3+2-1)$
2694	04432	$12-34+5^*67^*8-9A^*-B$	$B-A987-65^*-4^*3^*21$
2695	04433	$-1-2+3456-(78-9A^*-B)$	$-B^*(-A-98-76+5+432)^*-1$
2696	04434	$1234-5+678+9AB$	$-B-A-9-8^*7^*-65+4^*-32^*-1$
2697	04435	$1-2+3456-78+9A^*-B$	$-B-A987+(-65+43)^*-21$
2698	04436	$1234-5^*-6^*(78-9)-A^*B$	$-B+A-98-7-6^*5^*4^*32^*-1$
2699	04437	$-1-(-2-3456)-(-78-9A^*-B)$	$-B-A9-(87+6^*5^*4^*(-32-1))$
269A	04438	$-1+2345-6-7^*8^*-9^*(-A+B)$	$-B-A+987-6^*-5^*43^*-2^*-1$
269B	04439	$1+2+3456-78-9A^*B$	$B-A+9-87^*(-6+5-4-32)^*1$
26A0	04440	$12+3-45^*-67+89+AB$	$BA-(9-(876+5^*(432-1)))$
26A1	04441	$123-4-(5-6^*-7^*-89+AB)$	$B+A^*9^*8^*7^*(65-4+321)$
26A2	04442	$1234+56+(-78-9A)^*-B$	$-B-A9+8^*-7-6^*(-543-2)^*1$
26A3	04443	$1-23+45+6^*-78^*(-9-A+B)$	$-B-(A-987)-(-6-5^*432-1)$
26A4	04444	$1234+5+678+9AB$	$-B^*(-A9+87+6+5+4^*3^*-2)^*1$
26A5	04445	$-1-2^*3^*(-456+7-89+A-B)$	$BA+9-8+765^*4+32^*-1$
26A6	04446	$-1-2+3^*4^*5^*(67-8)-9^*(-A-B)$	$-BA+9+87-6^*(-543+21)$
26A7	04447	$1-234+56^*78-9A^*B$	$-B-A+987-6+5^*(432+1)$
26A8	04448	$1^*-2^*(-3^*-45-678-9AB)$	$BA9+8^*-7^*6-5^*-432+1$
26A9	04449	$-1-(-23+45^*-67)+89+AB$	$B+A+98+765^*4-3-21$
26AA	04450	$12+3456-78-9A^*B$	$B-A-(-98+765^*-4)-(-3^*2+1)$
26AB	04451	$1-23-4^*-567+89A+B$	$-B+A-(98-7-(-6^*5^*4^*-32+1))$
26B0	04452	$-12^*(3+4+5)^*(-67-89+AB)$	$-BA-98-(76+54^*3^*-21)$
26B1	04453	$1+2^*-3^*(45-(67^*-8+9AB))$	$B+A^*(9-8+76^*5-4-3)+2^*1$
26B2	04454	$1+2+3^*-4^*5^*(6-7)^*8^*9+AB$	$-B-A+987+6+5^*432^*1$
26B3	04455	$-1-(-2+3^*(-45-678))+9AB$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(-8-7-6-54^*3^*2^*1)$
26B4	04456	$-1^*(-23-45^*(-6+78)+9A+B)$	$-B+A9+8^*-7^*-65-(-43+21)$
26B5	04457	$-12-3+456^*7-(8-9+A+B)$	$BA9-8-7-654^*-3-21$
26B6	04458	$-1234-567^*-8-(9-AB)$	$-B+A98+765-4^*-321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
26B7	04459	$-1+2-3*(-4-5+6-7*8-9AB)$	$-B-A*(9+8-(-7+654)+321)$
26B8	04460	$-12-3+4*567+89A+B$	$-B-A9+(87-6*5+43)*21$
26B9	04461	$1-(-2345-(-6-7*-8*9))-(-A-B)$	$BA-9-8-765*-4-3-2+1$
26BA	04462	$1*(23-4)*(56-(-7+8))-(-9A-B)$	$BA-9*8*(-7-65-4+3+21)$
26BB	04463	$-123+4+5*(678-9-A-B)$	$BA+9-8+76*(-5-(43+2))*-1$
2700	04464	$1*-2*-3*-4*(-56+7-8-9+A*-B)$	$-BA-98*7*-6+5*(-43-2)-1$
2701	04465	$1-2345+6*7*89-A*-B$	$B-A-9*(-876-(-543+21))$
2702	04466	$-1-23+456*7*(8-9)*(A-B)$	$-BA+9-8-7-6*(543-2)*-1$
2703	04467	$-1-(-2-34+5+6*7*-89)-(-A-B)$	$-B+A9+8-765*-4+3-2*1$
2704	04468	$12-3*(-45-678)+9AB$	$BA+9+8*7*65+4+3+2*-1$
2705	04469	$12+3*(-4+56+78-9-A)*B$	$-B+A*(9-(-87+65*-4-3-21))$
2706	04470	$1-23+456*7-(8-9+A-B)$	$-B-A9-(8+7)-(6*-543+2)+1$
2707	04471	$-123-456*7+8+9+AB$	$-BA9+876*5-43+21$
2708	04472	$-1-23-4*(-5-6-789+A-B)$	$-B-A98-7*-654-321$
2709	04473	$123-45*6+7+8-(-9A+B)$	$-BA9+87+65*(4+3*21)$
270A	04474	$-1-23+4*567+8+9A*B$	$B+A-(987-65*(43+21))$
270B	04475	$-1+2-(3+4*567)-(-89A-B)$	$-B+A+987+6+5*432+1$
2710	04476	$1-23+4*567+8-9A*-B$	$B-A+987+6+5*-432*-1$
2711	04477	$-12-(-3456-78)-9AB$	$BA+9+87*(6-(-5+43)-2)*-1$
2712	04478	$-123+4-56*7-8-9AB$	$-BA9-8*(-7+6-543-2)-1$
2713	04479	$1*(-2+3-4)*(5-6-7-(-8+9AB))$	$B-(A+98+7-6*543+21)$
2714	04480	$12*34*(5-6-78-9-A*-B)$	$B+A98+765+4*321$
2715	04481	$-1+23-4*567+89A-B$	$BA9-(8+7)-(654*-3+2)+1$
2716	04482	$1*-23*(-45-6+7+8+9-AB)$	$-B-A-9-(87+6*(-543+2))-1$
2717	04483	$-1*(-2345+6*-78+9-A+B)$	$BA9-8-(7-654*3-2)-1$
2718	04484	$-1+2-(3-4*567+8+9A*-B)$	$B-A9+8-7+6*543-21$
2719	04485	$-1-2*3+4*(5+6+7+8+9-A-B)$	$B-(A-98-765*4)-(-3-21)$
271A	04486	$-1234-(5-6*789)-AB$	$B+A*-9+(-8-7+654)*(3+2*1)$
271B	04487	$-1234-56+7*-8*-9A+B$	$B-A98+76*(54+3)-2*-1$
2720	04488	$-1-2+3456+78-9AB$	$BA-9+8-(765*-4-3*2-1)$
2721	04489	$12+3+456*7+8-9-A-B$	$BA9+8-7+(65-4)*32+1$
2722	04490	$1-2-(-3456-78+9AB)$	$-BA9+876*5-4-3*(2-1)$
2723	04491	$1-(-23-45)+6*7*-89*(A-B)$	$-BA+987-65*(-4-32)*1$
2724	04492	$-1+2+3456+78-9AB$	$B+A-(-9-87)*(6+5)*4-321$
2725	04493	$1-2+3+456*7+8-(9-A)*-B$	$BA+98*7*-6-54-321$
2726	04494	$-12*3*(-45-6+78-9-AB)$	$B-A98+7*654-321$
2727	04495	$1+2-3+456*7*(-8+9)-A+B$	$BA9-8+7+654*3-2+1$
2728	04496	$123+4*(-5+6+789)-AB$	$B-A+98-765*-4+32+1$
2729	04497	$1-234-5*(-678-9)+A-B$	$BA9+876+543*2*1$
272A	04498	$-1-23-4*(-567-8)+9A*B$	$BA9+8-7-654*3*(-2+1)$
272B	04499	$12-34+5+6*7*89-A*-B$	$BA-9-(-8-765)*4-(3+2)-1$
2730	04500	$-12+3-(4-(-5+6*-7*-89)-A*B)$	$-B+A*-9+(8-7)*6*543-21$
2731	04501	$12+34-(5-6*7*(89-A+B))$	$B-A*(9-8-(7+6)-(-5*-4+321))$
2732	04502	$-12+3456+(-7+8+9)*-AB$	$-BA9+876*5+4*(3-2)+1$
2733	04503	$-1-(-23-4*567-89A-B)$	$B-A9+8-7+6*(543-(2-1))$
2734	04504	$-1-2-3-45*(-67-8)+9-A*B$	$BA+98*7*6-5*43*-2*-1$
2735	04505	$12+3456-(-78+9AB)$	$-BA9+876*5+4*(-3-(2-1))$
2736	04506	$1+2345-(-6*78-(-9+A)-B)$	$-BA+9+8+7-(-6*543+2)*1$
2737	04507	$-1-2+34*56*7-89A*B$	$-B-A-(98+7-6*543-21)$
2738	04508	$-12*(-345+6+7+89-A-B)$	$BA9-8*(76-5)*-4+3*21$
2739	04509	$-12+3-456*-7-(89-AB)$	$B-A-9-(87+6*(-543+2-1))$
273A	04510	$12-34-5+6*7*-89+AB$	$B*(-A9-(-8+7-(-65+432)))+1$
273B	04511	$-1+2-34*56*-7-89A*B$	$BA9-(-8-76*(5+43-21))$
2740	04512	$1-2-(-3456+7+8-9A*-B)$	$BA9+8+7-654*3*(-2+1)$
2741	04513	$-12+3456-(-7+8)-9A*B$	$B+A-98+7+6*543-21$
2742	04514	$-1+2+3456-7-8-9A*B$	$BA9+8-7*(-6+54-321)$
2743	04515	$-1-(-23-45*(67+8))+9-AB$	$B-A*-9+8*-7*-65-43*-2*1$
2744	04516	$1*-2*(-34-567+8-9AB)$	$-BA9-8+7*(654-32+1)$
2745	04517	$-1+2+3+456*7+8+(9-A)*-B$	$B-(A+98-(7-6*-543))-(-2+1)$
2746	04518	$-1*2*-3*(456+7+89+A-B)$	$B-A-9-8-7-6*-543+21$
2747	04519	$(1+(2+3)^4+5*6)*7-8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8-7+6*543+21$
2748	04520	$1+2-(3-456*7)-(89-AB)$	$BA+9-8+765*4+32-1$
2749	04521	$-1+23*-4+5*(678-9-A-B)$	$BA9-(8-7)-(-654*3-21)$
274A	04522	$-12+3*(4-(5+6))-(-78-9AB))$	$-BA-9-87+6*(543+21)$
274B	04523	$-1*(-2345+6*-78-9-(A+B))$	$-BA9+876*5+43-21$
2750	04524	$-12+3456-7-89A-B$	$BA-98*7*6-5432*-1$
2751	04525	$-1+((-2+3^4+5)*-6-7+8)*-9+A-B$	$-B+A98-76+5*432*-1$
2752	04526	$-1-2+3456-(7-8)-9A*B$	$B-A+987+6*(54+321)$
2753	04527	$-123+45*(-6+78)-(-9-AB)$	$B+A9+8-765*-4+32+1$
2754	04528	$-1+2345+6*(7-89)*(A-B)$	$BA+9-(8+765)*-4-(3+2)*-1$
2755	04529	$-1+2*-3*(-456-7-(89-A+B))$	$-B+A-98+7+654*(3+2)-1$
2756	04530	$-1+23-45*(-67-8)-9A+B$	$-B-A-9-8-(-7+6*5*-4*32-1)$
2757	04531	$12-3+456*7-89+AB$	$B-A*(-98-76-5*4)*(3-2+1)$
2758	04532	$1-2345-6*(7+8-9AB)$	$-BA9+8+7*(654-32+1)$
2759	04533	$-1234+56*(-7+89)+AB$	$B+A-(9+87)+6*543-2*1$
275A	04534	$123-45+6*-78*(-9-A+B)$	$BA-9*-8-76*(-5-(4+32+1))$
275B	04535	$-1-2+3456-7-89A-B$	$B+A-9+(-8+7*6)*(5+4^3*2)+1$
2760	04536	$-12*(-3-(-4-5))*6*(-7+8-(9-A)-B)$	$-B-A+9-8-7*6*543+21$
2761	04537	$1-2+3456-7-(89A+B)$	$B+A-9-8+7*6^5/4/3-2-1$
2762	04538	$-123-456*-7+89-A*-B$	$-B-(-A+9+87-6*543)+21$
2763	04539	$-1+2+3456-7-89A-B$	$-BA-98+765*4+321$
2764	04540	$123+45*6+7+8+9+A*B$	$-BA+9-(87-6*(543+21))$
2765	04541	$1+2+3456-7-89A-B$	$-BA-(98+7-6+54*-3*21)$
2766	04542	$1-(2-3-(4-(5-6*-7*-89)))+AB$	$B+A-9-8+7*6^5/4/3+2*1$
2767	04543	$12+3456-7+8-9A*B$	$-B*(-A9+87+6-(-54+321))$
2768	04544	$-123+4*(56+789)+A-B$	$BA*(98-7-65)*(-4+3)*(-2+1)$
2769	04545	$-123-4+(56-7)*8*(9-(A-B))$	$-BA9-876*-5+43-(2+1)$
276A	04546	$-12+3456-(7+89A-B)$	$-BA9-876*-5+43-2*1$
276B	04547	$1-2*-3-4*-5*(6-(-78-9A-B))$	$B-(A-9)-(87-654*(-3-2))*-1$
2770	04548	$-1*-2*(34-(-567-8-9AB))$	$B+A98-76+5*432+1$
2771	04549	$123-45+6*-7*-89+A+B$	$B-(-A+9+87+654*(3+2)*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2772	04550	-12+3+4*5-6*-7*89+AB	-BA9+8*-7*6*-5*4-321
2773	04551	12-3+4*(-5+6-(-789-A-B))	-BA9-8*(7+6-543-21)
2774	04552	12+3456-7-89A-B	BA9+87-6*(5-4-321)
2775	04553	-123-4*567-8*9*A*-B	-BA-9-(-87-6*543)-21
2776	04554	1+2-3456-7+8*9A*B	BA-9*-8-765*-4+3-2-1
2777	04555	1+2+3456-(-7+89A)-B	-BA+9*8-7+6*(543+2-1)
2778	04556	-1+2+3456-78-9*-AB	-B-(-A-(9-87)-6*543-21)
2779	04557	-1-2+3456-7-89A+B	-B+A*-9*-8*7-(6+5)-(-4+321)
277A	04558	-1*(2-(3456-7)-(-89A+B))	BA9+87+6*(-5+4)*-321
277B	04559	-1+2345-6-(7*-89-A*-B)	BA+98+765*4-(32+1)
2780	04560	-12+3456+7-89A+B	BA+98-765*-4+32*-1
2781	04561	1-(-2345+6-7*89-A*-B)	B+A*(9+876-543-21)
2782	04562	-1234+5-6+7*-8*-9A+B	-B-A9-8-76+54*3*-21
2783	04563	1+2-(-3456+7+89A-B)	-BA9-8-(765-4321)
2784	04564	-1+2345-(67*-8+9)-(A-B)	-BA9-8-76+5*43*21
2785	04565	-12-3+4*567-(-8-9A)*B	B*(-A9+8+76+54*-3*2)*-1
2786	04566	12+3456+7-89A-B	-B+A+9+8-7*(65-43)*-21
2787	04567	-12+3-45+6*7*(-8+9A)+B	-BA-9+8-76+54*3*-21
2788	04568	-12+3456-789-AB	-BA-(-98+7+6*-543)-21
2789	04569	12+3456-78-9*AB	-B-(-A+9-87-6*(543-21))
278A	04570	-1+2-(34+56*-7*(-8+9)*A+B)	-B-A-9-8+7-6*-543-21
278B	04571	-1-2-(-3456-(7-89A)-B)	-B-A9+87+6*(543-(2+1))
2790	04572	-12+34+5+6*-7*-89+AB	-B-A9+8+7*-6*(5+43)*-2*1
2791	04573	1-2+3456+7-89A+B	-B-A-(98+76)+54*3*21
2792	04574	12+3456-7-89A+B	BA+9+8-765*-4+3*21
2793	04575	12+3-45*(-6-(78+9-A-B))	BA9+87-(654*-3+21)
2794	04576	-1+2-3+456*7+89-A-B	-B*(A+9+87+65-432-1)
2795	04577	1+2+3456+7-89A+B	B+A+9+8+7*6^5/4/3+2+1
2796	04578	123-4-5+6*(-7*-89-A+B)	-B-A9+87+6*(543-2)+1
2797	04579	-1-2+3456-789-AB	-BA9+8-765+4321
2798	04580	-1-234+5*678+9A+B	-BA9+8-76+5*43*21
2799	04581	1-2+3456-789-AB	-B-A-9-(8-76-5)*(43+2)*1
279A	04582	-12+3-456*-7-8+9A-B	-B+A9+8*-7*-65+4*-32*-1
279B	04583	-1+2+3456-789-AB	B+A+(9*8*7-6+5+4)*3^2-1
27A0	04584	1+2345-6*(7+8+9-AB)	-BA-9+87-6*(-543-2+1)
27A1	04585	1+2-(-3456+789+AB)	-BA+9+8-76+54*3*-21
27A2	04586	12-3*(-4+5-6-(78+9AB))	-B+A+(98-7-6*-5)*(-4+32-1)
27A3	04587	-1-23+456*7-8+9A+B	-B*(-A98+765+43+2+1)
27A4	04588	1+2*-345+67*8*9-AB	-B-(A9-87-6*543)-(2-1)
27A5	04589	1-23-4*-567-(8-9AB)	-B-A9+87+6*-543*(-2+1)
27A6	04590	1*-23*(-45+6-(-7+8-9+AB))	BA-(9+87)+6*5*4*-32*-1
27A7	04591	12-3*(4+56)*(-7-8)+9AB	-BA-(-98+7)-6*(543-2*-1)
27A8	04592	-1-2*3*(4-567+8)-9A-B	-BA+98-7+6*543-2+1
27A9	04593	1-234+5*678+9+AB	BA-9-8*7*65-4*(-32+1)
27AA	04594	-1-2-3*-4+(56-(78+9))*-AB	B-A-(9-(8-7+6*543))-21
27AB	04595	12+3-456*-7+89-A-B	BA-987+65*(43+21)
27B0	04596	1-23+45*(-6-(-78+9-A)))+B	BA9-87*-6-5*(4-321)
27B1	04597	-12+3+456*7-(8+9)+AB	-B-A-(-9+8+7-(-6*-543-2*1))
27B2	04598	1-2-3+(-45-6)*7*8-9A*-B	BA9+87+654*3+2*-1
27B3	04599	-1*(23+4*(-5+6-7*-8-9))*(-A-B)	-BA9-876*-5+43*2*1
27B4	04600	12+34+5+6*7*89+AB	BA9+87+654*-3*(-2+1)
27B5	04601	1+2345+6*78+9A-B	BA9+87+654*3+2-1
27B6	04602	1-2-(-3456+789)-A*B	B-A*(9-8-76*5)+43*2-1
27B7	04603	1+234-5-6*7*-89-AB	BA+98+765*4+3+2*1
27B8	04604	-123+4-(-5*678-9*(A-B))	BA98-7*6*5*(-43-21)
27B9	04605	1-23-4*-567+8+9AB	BA+987-6-5*-432*1
27BA	04606	-1234+5+6*789-A-B	-B-(-A-9)-8-7-(6*(-543+2)+1)
27BB	04607	-123+4+56*78+9A*-B	B+A+9-8*7*6+(5+4*3)^(2+1)
2800	04608	-1-2+3-456*-7-8-9+AB	B-A9+87-(6*-543+2+1)
2801	04609	1+23-4+(-56+78+9)*AB	-B*(A9-8+76*5-4*32)*-1
2802	04610	-123-4-5*(67+8)*(-9A)*-B	B-(A-9+8)+7-(6*-543+21)
2803	04611	-1-234-5*(-6-789+AB)	-B-A*-9-87*(-6-(-5+4)-(32+1))
2804	04612	1+2+34*5+6*7*89+A-B	-B-A-9-(-8-7-(-6*-543+2)+1)
2805	04613	-1-234-5-(-6*78*9A+B)	B+A+98*7*6-5*43-21
2806	04614	-1*2*-3*(-4-(-567-89)-AB)	-B-A9+87+6*543+21
2807	04615	-123-4-5*-678-(-9+A-B)	-B+A-9+8-7-6*-543+2*-1
2808	04616	-1-23-(-4-5*678)-9-AB	BA+987-(-6-5*432)-1
2809	04617	-1+23-(-4+5*67*-8-9AB)	BA+987+6-5*432*-1
280A	04618	-12+3456-7-8-9*AB	-B-A+98*(7-6+5-4+32)-1
280B	04619	-12-3-(4-5*678)-(-9+AB)	-B-(-A+9-(8-7+6*543-2*-1))
2810	04620	12*(3+45+6+78-9A)*B	-B*(A98-765-43)*(-2+1)
2811	04621	-1-(23-4-56*78+9AB)	BA+98*-7*6-(-54+321)
2812	04622	-1+234-5+6*7*89-A*B	-BA-A9-8-76*(-5-43+2+1)
2813	04623	1+2+3456+78+9A*-B	-BA-98*-7*6-5-43*2*1
2814	04624	-12-3-4+56*78-9AB	-B-A*(-987+654)-3*21
2815	04625	-123+4+5*678-(9-A-B)	B-A9+87-654*(3+2)*-1
2816	04626	-1-2*-3*(45+678)-9AB	-BA-9+8-7+6*(543+21)
2817	04627	-1+2345-6-7*(8-(9A-B))	-B+A98-(-7-6-5*432+1)
2818	04628	1-(2-3-456*7+8-9-AB)	-B-(-A98-7)+6*5*-432*1
2819	04629	-123-4+5*(678+9)-(A+B)	-BA-98*7*-6-54-32+1
281A	04630	-12+3-4+56*78-9AB	-B-A-(-9-8)-(-7-6*543-2+1)
281B	04631	-12+3+456*7+8-(-9-AB)	B+A98-7+6+5*(432-1)
2820	04632	1-2+3*-4+56*78-9AB	B-A+98*7*(-6*-5-(-432-1))
2821	04633	1-2*-3*4*(5-(-6+7*(89-AB)))	-B-A9-8*7*-65-(-4-321)
2822	04634	12+3456+78+9A*-B	BA9+8+765-4*-321
2823	04635	1+2+3456-(7+8+9*AB)	-BA+9*87-65*(-43+2-1)
2824	04636	12+3-45*(-67-8)-(-9-A+B)	B+A98-7+6+5*-432*-1
2825	04637	1*-234+567*8-9AB	-BA9+8+7*(654+3-21)
2826	04638	1-234+567*8-9AB	-B-A+9-8+7-6*-543+21
2827	04639	-12+3*(45-(-67-8)-9A)*B	-B-A*(-987+654+3+2+1)
2828	04640	1+2345-(-6*(-7+89)-A*B)	-BA-9+(-8+76)*54-321

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2829	04641	-1+23-4*-567-8+9AB	-B+A9-87-6*543*(-2+1)
282A	04642	1*23+4*567-8+9AB	-B+A9-87-6*-543+2-1
282B	04643	1-23-(4-5*678+9A-B)	B-A*-9*87+6*(-543-2)*1
2830	04644	-1*23*(-45+6-(-7-8+9))-AB)	BA-9-87-6*(543-2)*-1
2831	04645	1+2345-(-6+78*-9+AB)	B-(-A98-7-6-5*(432-1))
2832	04646	12+3+4+5*(678-9)-A*B	BA-98-7-(6*-543-2+1)
2833	04647	-1+2+3456+7-8-9*AB	BA-98-7+6*543-2*-1
2834	04648	-1234+5-6*-789-(-A-B)	-B-(A-98+7)+6*5*-4*-32*1
2835	04649	-1+2+3456-(7-8)-9*AB	BA+9-87-6*-543-21
2836	04650	-1-2-3*(-45-(67-8)-9AB)	-B-A98+76*54+321
2837	04651	1-2-3+4-5*-678-9A-B	BA9-87*-6*5-4*32*1
2838	04652	-12-(-3+45+6*(7+8-9))*-AB)	BA9+87*6*5+4*-32+1
2839	04653	12+3-4+5*678-9-AB	B+A*9*8-7-65*-43+2*1
283A	04654	1*2*(-3-45+678+9AB)	B-A+9-(-8-7+6*-543)+2+1
283B	04655	12-3*-45*67+8*9*-A*B	-BA9+8*(7-6)*(543+21)
2840	04656	-1-23+4+5*(-6+789+A*-B)	BA-9-87+6*543*(2-1)
2841	04657	1-23+4-5*-678+9*-A-B	-B+A98-7*-6+5*432*1
2842	04658	12-(-3+4)-(-56*78+9AB)	B-A-9+8+7-6*-543+21
2843	04659	-1+2-34*5+6*-78*-9+A*-B	B+A9+8-(7-6*(543+21))
2844	04660	12+3456-(-7+8-9*-AB)	B+A9+8-7+6*543+2+1
2845	04661	-1-2345-678*-9+A-B	BA9+8-7*6*(-54-3*2*1)
2846	04662	1-2-3*-4-5*-678-(9A+B)	BA+9-87-6*(-543+2)*1
2847	04663	1-2345+678*9-(-A+B)	B+A-9+(-8+7)*-6*543+21
2848	04664	1-(2-34-5*(678-9))-A*-B)	B*(-A+98)*(76-54+3-21)
2849	04665	1+2+3456+7+8-9*AB	B+A9-87+6*543-2*-1
284A	04666	1-(-2345-6)-(-78*9-A*-B)	-B+A9-(87+6*-543-21)
284B	04667	-1+23-4*5-67*(-8*-9-AB)	-BA9-8-(-7-6)+5*-43*-21
2850	04668	1+234-5*-67*8-9*-AB	BA+9-87-6*(-543+2-1)
2851	04669	-1+2345-6+7*89*(-A+B)	B+A9-87-6*(-543-(2-1))
2852	04670	-123+45-6*-7*(-8-9+AB)	-BA-98*7*-6-(54-3-2+1)
2853	04671	1*-23*(4+567+8*(9-AB))	-BA9-(-8-7+6)+5*43*21
2854	04672	12-(-3-4)-(5*678+9A)-B	B-(A98+76*-54)+321
2855	04673	-1+2+3-4+5*678-(9A-B)	BA9-87-6-5*-432-1
2856	04674	-1*2*-3*(456+7-(-8+9)+AB)	-BA-9*-87*6-(543-21)
2857	04675	123+45*(67+8)-9A+B	B*(-A9-87-6-5*43)*21
2858	04676	-12+3-45*(6-78)-(-9A-B)	-BA-9*8+76+54*3*21
2859	04677	1+23+4-(-56*78+9AB)	BA+9-(87-6*543-(2+1))
285A	04678	-12+3456-789-A-B	-BA-9-8-7*(-65-432*1)
285B	04679	1-2+34-5*-678-(9+AB)	-BA+9-8+(76+5)*43-21
2860	04680	1*2*(-3-4+5)*(6+7+8-9*AB)	B+A98+7*6-5*-432+1
2861	04681	1+2345-67*8-(-9A+B)	-B+A-9-87-6+54*-3*-21
2862	04682	1-23-4*-567+8*-9*(-A-B)	-BA+9*8*(76-5+4+3-21)
2863	04683	1+2345+6-7*-89*(-A+B)	BA-9-(-87+65)*(4+3)*21
2864	04684	-1-23+4*(-56-(-789-AB))	B-A-(98+7-6+54*3*21)
2865	04685	-1-2-(3-(456*7+8)+9*(-A-B))	B-(A-98)-(-7+6*5*4*-32)+1
2866	04686	-12+3-4+5*678+9*-A+B	BA9-8-76-(-5*432-1)
2867	04687	12-3*-4-5*-678-(9A*-B)	-B-A-9+87-6*(-543-2*-1)
2868	04688	1+2+34-56*-78-9AB	B+A9-87+6*543+21
2869	04689	-1-2-(-3456-(-789-A-B))	B-A9+8-7+6-54*-3*21
286A	04690	-12*(-34-56-(-7-(-89-AB)))	-B-A+9-8*-7+6*543-2*1
286B	04691	1-2+3456-(789+A)-B	BA-9*8+7+6*(-543+2)*-1
2870	04692	1-(-23+45*(-6-7+8+9+A+B))	-BA-98+76*(5+43-(2-1))
2871	04693	-1-(-2-3456)-(-789-(-A-B))	-B+A9+8+7-6*-5*4*32*1
2872	04694	1*2+3456-789-A-B	-B-A+9*-8-(7+6+54*3*-21)
2873	04695	1+2-(-3456+789)-(-A+B)	B-A-9-87-(-6+54*-3*21)
2874	04696	-1-(-2+3-4+5*(678-9))-AB	B+A*-9-8+7+6*(543+21)
2875	04697	1*-2+3456-7-8*(9+AB)	-B*(A-9-8)*(-7-6-5+4+3*21)
2876	04698	-12+3456-789+A-B	BA9+8*76-5*(4-321)
2877	04699	-12+3456+789*(A-B)	-B+A*(987-654)-3-(-2-1)
2878	04700	-12+3456-(789+A-B)	B+A98+7-6*(-54-321)
2879	04701	1-2-(-3*-4-5*(678-9))-A-B	BA9+8-(76-5*432*-1)
287A	04702	1-2+3456-7*-8+9*-AB	BA9+8-(76+5*432)+1
287B	04703	1+2+3*45-(6*-7*89-AB)	B+A-9-87-6-54*3*-21
2880	04704	-12*-3*-4*(5-6-7-8+9-(A+B))	-B+A98+76-5*-432-1
2881	04705	1-(-23-4)-(5*-678+9A-B)	BA-(-9-87*(6+5)*4+3-21)
2882	04706	12-(-3456+789)-A-B	-B-(-A98-76)-(-5*432-1)
2883	04707	-12-(3+4*567)+8*9*-A*-B	B+A-9*8*(-7-6)*5-4*3/-2*1
2884	04708	-1-23-4-5*(-678+9A-B)	B*(A9-8+76+54*3+21)
2885	04709	1+2345+678-9*(A+B)	-B+A98+7+65*(4+32-1)
2886	04710	-12-3*4*-5*67-(8-(-9-A+B))	-B+A-(9+8*7)-6*(-543-21)
2887	04711	1-2-(-3456+789-A)-B	BA-9+(-87-6)*(-54-(3-21))
2888	04712	1-2-(-3456-789*(A-B))	-BA9+8-7*-6-5*43*-21
2889	04713	-1-(-2-3456)-(-789-A+B)	B+A9-(-8*-7+6*-543-(2+1))
288A	04714	-1+2-(-3456-789*(A-B))	BA9+8*(-76-5)*-4-32-1
288B	04715	1+2+3456-(789-A)-B	-B-A+98-7+6*543+2-1
2890	04716	-1*(-2-3456+789+A-B)	-B-A-(-98*7+65*-43+2*1)
2891	04717	12+3456+7*8-9*AB	-B-(A98+765)+4321
2892	04718	12*(-3-(456-789))-AB)	B-A9-8-7*(-65-432-1)
2893	04719	1+2345-67+8*(9A-B)	B+A9+87+6*(543-21)
2894	04720	-12+3456-(789-A-B)	-B-(-A9-8)-(-7-(6*543-21))
2895	04721	-1-234*(-5-6)+789-(A-B)	-BA-9+8*(7-6-5-(-432+1))
2896	04722	-12+3+45*(67+8)-9+AB	B-A-98+7*(65+432)*1
2897	04723	-1+2+3456-78*(-9+A+B)	-B+A98+7*(6-5-4+321)
2898	04724	-12-3*-45*-6*7-8*-9AB	-BA+98*7*-6*(-5+4)-3-(2+1)
2899	04725	1*(2+3-(4-56+78))*-9*(A+B)	-B+A-(-9-87)+6*(543-2)*1
289A	04726	1-23+(456-78-9A)*B	BA9-8*7-6+5*(432+1)
289B	04727	-1234-5-6*-789-A*-B	B+A98+76+5*-432*-1
28A0	04728	12+3456-(789-(-A+B))	-B+A9-(-8+7-6*543)-(2-1)
28A1	04729	12+3+4*(-56+789+AB)	BA+9+(-87-6)*(-54-3+21)
28A2	04730	1+2-3-456*-7+89+AB	B+A*-9*(-8+7)-6*-543+2+1
28A3	04731	-1-2-(-3456+789-A-B)	-B+A*987+6-5432*1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
28A4	04732	$12^*(-3+4-5-678-9A^*-B)$	$B+A-(-9+8+76-54^*-3^*-21)$
28A5	04733	$12+34+5^*678-9^*A-B$	$B+A9-8-7+6^*(543-2-1)$
28A6	04734	$12-34^*(56-7)^*(8-9+A-B)$	$BA9-8-7^*6+5^*432+1$
28A7	04735	$-1+2-34-(-56^*78+9A^*B)$	$B+A+9-8^*-7^*(-6+5^*4)^*3^*2+1$
28A8	04736	$123+456^*7-8^*-9-(-A+B)$	$-BA9-8-7^*-654-(32+1)$
28A9	04737	$1+2345+67^*-8+9AB$	$-BA9-8+7^*654+32^*-1$
28AA	04738	$-12-3^*4^*-56^*(-7-8+9)^*(A-B)$	$-B-A+987-6^*5^*4^*(-3-21)$
28AB	04739	$1-2-34^*-56+(-7-8)^*(-9-AB)$	$B-A98-765+4321$
28B0	04740	$12+34-56^*7^*-8+9^*-A^*-B$	$B+A9^*-8+76^*54+(-3+2)^*-1$
28B1	04741	$1+2-3^*45^*6^*7-8^*-9AB$	$BA+98-(-7+6^*(-543+21))$
28B2	04742	$12-34+5^*678+9-A-B$	$-B-A9-8+76-54^*-3^*21$
28B3	04743	$-1+23^*4+5-6^*-7^*(-8+9A)+B$	$-BA-(-98+7)+6^*(543+21)$
28B4	04744	$12-34-5^*-678-(9-A+B)$	$-B+A9-8-7+654^*(3+2)+1$
28B5	04745	$-1-2^*-3+4^*(5-67+89A-B)$	$-BA+98^*-7^*-6-(-5-4-3^*2^*1)$
28B6	04746	$12-34+5^*678-(9+A-B)$	$BA+9-8^*7-6^*-543+21$
28B7	04747	$-123-45^*-67+8^*-9^*-A+B$	$-BA9-8-7^*-654-3-21$
28B8	04748	$12+3456-789+A+B$	$-B-A9-8^*(-76-(54+321))$
28B9	04749	$123-456^*-7+89-A-B$	$-B+A9+87+6^*(-543-2)^*-1$
28BA	04750	$1-2-3^*(-4^*-5-6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA+9^*8-(-7-65)^*(43+2+1)$
28BB	04751	$-1+2-34+5^*678+9-A+B$	$B-A-(-98-7+6^*-543-2+1)$
2900	04752	$1^*-2^*(34+56+78)^*(9-A-B)$	$B+A9-8+7-6^*(-543+2)-1$
2901	04753	$12+3456+78+9^*-AB$	$-BA9-8-7^*-654+3-21$
2902	04754	$-1^*2^*(-3-(-4-(5-678-9AB)))$	$-B-A^*-98-7^*(6-54-321)$
2903	04755	$1+2-(34+5^*-678-(-9+A+B))$	$B+A-9+87-654^*(-3-2)^*1$
2904	04756	$12+3+4-5^*(678-9)^*(A-B)$	$BA-9-8+7-6^*-543+2^*-1$
2905	04757	$-1^*(-23+456^*-7-(89+AB))$	$B-A-(-9-87+6^*(-543-2-1))$
2906	04758	$-1234+5+6^*789+AB$	$-B+A-9^*-8+7+6^*-5^*4^*(-32-1)$
2907	04759	$-12+345^*6-7-(-8-9)^*-A^*-B$	$B+A+98-7+6^*543+2+1$
2908	04760	$-1-23-4^*(5+67-(89A+B))$	$-BA9+8+76+5^*-43^*-21$
2909	04761	$-123+4^*(-5-(6-789-AB))$	$B-(A-98)-(7+6^*-543)+21$
290A	04762	$1^*2^*(-3-4-(-5-(678+9AB)))$	$-BA9+8+7^*65^*4^*3-2+1$
290B	04763	$12-3-4+5^*(678-9)+A+B$	$B^*(A-(-987+654)-(3+21))$
2910	04764	$12-34+5^*678+9-(A-B)$	$B-(A9+8-7-6^*543)-(2-1)$
2911	04765	$1+2345-6+78^*9-A+B$	$BA+9^*87+65^*(43-(2+1))$
2912	04766	$1+2+3+45^*6^*(7+8)-(9-(A-B))$	$-B-A98+7^*-6+5^*43^*21$
2913	04767	$-1-(-2345-678)-(9A+B)$	$-BA-(9+87^*-6^*5)-4^*-321$
2914	04768	$1+23-45^*(-67-8)+9A+B$	$-BA-98^*-7^*6+(-5+4)^*32^*-1$
2915	04769	$1+2345-(-678+9A+B)$	$B+A9-(8-(7+6^*(543+2+1)))$
2916	04770	$1^*2^*(-34-5)^*(-67-(89-AB))$	$B-A9+8^*(76+54+321)$
2917	04771	$-1-2+3456-7-(-89+A)^*-B$	$-BA9+87-(-6+5^*-43^*21)$
2918	04772	$-1+2-34-5^*(-6-7)^*8^*9+A+B$	$BA+9+8-7+6^*(543-(2-1))$
2919	04773	$-123+4+5^*(6+789-AB)$	$-B-(A-98)-(7-(-6^*-543+21))$
291A	04774	$-1+2345+678+9-AB$	$B^*(A-9-8+7+6)^*(-5-43+21)$
291B	04775	$1+2+3456+7-(89^*A+B)$	$B-A+9-(-8+765)^*-4+321$
2920	04776	$1+2345+678+9-AB$	$BA9-8-(-7+6-5^*432^*1)$
2921	04777	$-1-2+3456-(7-89^*-A)+B$	$-B-A+9-8-765^*-4+321$
2922	04778	$12+345-6^*-7^*89-AB$	$-BA-98^*7^*-6-(5-43-2^*1)$
2923	04779	$1+2345+678-9-A^*B$	$-B+A98-7^*-65^*(4+3-(2-1))$
2924	04780	$-12+3456+7-89^*A+B$	$-BA9-(8+7^*-654)-(3^*-2+1)$
2925	04781	$12-3^*(-4-56-78-9AB)$	$B+A9-(-8-7)-6^*-543^*(2-1)$
2926	04782	$12-34^*5-6^*-78^*-9^*(A-B)$	$BA-98^*(-7+6^*-5-4+3+2^*-1)$
2927	04783	$12-3+4-5^*-678+9-A-B$	$BA-9-8+7+6^*543+21$
2928	04784	$1+2+3+4-56^*-78-9A^*B$	$-BA9-8-7^*-654+3^*(2+1)$
2929	04785	$12-(3-4)-(5^*-678+9-A+B)$	$-B+A98-76^*(-54-(-3-21))$
292A	04786	$123+456^*7-(8-(9A+B))$	$-BA9-(-8+7^*-654)-(-3^*-2-1)$
292B	04787	$1-(-234-5^*6^*7^*8)+9A^*B$	$BA9+8+7^*(-65+4)^*(-3-(2+1))$
2930	04788	$-123^*(-45+6-7-89+AB)$	$BA9+876+5+4^*321$
2931	04789	$-1+2345+678-9A+B$	$B-A-98^*7^*-6-5-4+3^*-21$
2932	04790	$-123-4+567^*8-9AB$	$B+A9-8+7-6^*-543+21$
2933	04791	$-1-2+3456+7+89^*-A+B$	$B-(A9-87-6-54^*3^*21)$
2934	04792	$-1-23-4^*(56-78-9^*A+B)$	$BA9+8+7-6-5^*432^*-1$
2935	04793	$1+2+3+4^*-56+7^*-8^*-9^*A+B$	$-B-A-(-9-8-765^*4-321)$
2936	04794	$12+34-5^*(-678+9-(-A+B))$	$B+A+(98-7^*6)^*54+32-1$
2937	04795	$-1+2345+678-(9-A^*-B)$	$BA-98-7-6^*(-543-21)$
2938	04796	$-123+4-56-(-7^*-8^*9^*-A+B)$	$-BA+9^*8^*76+543^*2^*-1$
2939	04797	$1+2345+678-(9^*-A+B)$	$-BA9+876^*5-4^*-3^*21$
293A	04798	$-12-(-34+5^*-678-(-9-A)-B)$	$B-A-98+(7+6-5)^*432+1$
293B	04799	$1+2345-6+7-8^*(-9A+B)$	$BA-9+8-(-7-6^*543-21)$
2940	04800	$-12-(-3456-78^*(-9+A)^*-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7-6+(5+4^3)^*2^*1$
2941	04801	$12+3456-7+8^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A-9-8-765^*-4+321$
2942	04802	$12+3456+7+(89-A)^*-B$	$BA9+87^*-6^*-5-4-3^*(-2+1)$
2943	04803	$123+4^*(56+789-A-B)$	$BA9-87^*(6-54-(-3-21))$
2944	04804	$1^*2-(3+45)+6^*-78^*-9-A^*B$	$B-A-(9^*-876-5^*-43^*21)$
2945	04805	$12-(-3-(-45-6^*7^*(-89-A)))+B$	$B+A-9-8+7-6+54^*3^*21$
2946	04806	$1^*2^*-3^*(-4-567-8+9-A+B)$	$B-A^*(-987-6)-(5432+1)$
2947	04807	$1+2^*3+4^*(-56-(-7-89A)-B)$	$-B^*(A98+765-(4-32^*1))$
2948	04808	$12+3456+7-(-89^*-A-B)$	$BA-(-9-8^*7-(6^*543-21))$
2949	04809	$-12+3456-789+A^*B$	$-B+A9-87-6-54^*3^*-21$
294A	04810	$-1^*(23+4-5)^*(-67-89-(-A+B))$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7^*-6^*5+4^3)^*2+1$
294B	04811	$-12+34+5^*(-67-8^*(-9+A))^*-B$	$BA+98-7-6^*5^*4^*-32^*1$
2950	04812	$-1+2345+6+7^*89+AB$	$-BA+98-7^*(-65-432)+1$
2951	04813	$12+3+4-5^*-678-9+A+B$	$BA-98-7-6-54^*3^*-21$
2952	04814	$-12+34+5^*678+9+A-B$	$-BA9-8-7^*-654+32+1$
2953	04815	$1-(2+3-(456-78)^*9)-AB$	$B-(A-98^*7^*6)-(54-(3+2+1))$
2954	04816	$-1-(-2345+67-8^*9A)+B$	$BA9-8^*7-(-65-4)^*(32+1)$
2955	04817	$1-(-2345-6^*-78-9AB)$	$-BA-9-87+(6+5)^*(4+321)$
2956	04818	$123-4-(-5^*678+9A+B)$	$B-A+98^*7^*6-5^*-4-3^*21$
2957	04819	$1-(-2345-678)-9^*A+B$	$B+A+9-8-(765^*-4-321)$
2958	04820	$12-34-5^*(-678-9)-(-A-B)$	$-BA+9^*8+76+54^*3^*21$
2959	04821	$1+23+4-(-5^*678-9^*(-A+B))$	$-B+A9-87+6-54^*-3^*21$
295A	04822	$-1-(-2-3456-(-7-8+9^*-A^*B))$	$B+A98-765^*(4-3)^*(-2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
295B	04823	$(1*2*3*(4+5)+6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA-98-765*-4+321$
2960	04824	$12+34+5*678-9+A-B$	$B+A+9*876-5*43*21$
2961	04825	$-1-2-3*4+5*(678-9+A+B)$	$BA9-8-(-7-(65-4))*(32+1)$
2962	04826	$123+4+5*678-9A-B$	$BA+98*(7+6)-54*-3*21$
2963	04827	$-123+4+56*7*8-9A*-B$	$-B+A+98*7*6+(-5+43-2)*-1$
2964	04828	$1+23+4+5*(678-9+A)+B$	$BA-9+8*7+654*(3+2)-1$
2965	04829	$1-(-2345+6-7*(8+9A))+B$	$-B*(A-987-(-654+3-21))$
2966	04830	$-12-(-3456+789)+AB$	$-BA9+8+7*654+32+1$
2967	04831	$-1+2345-6*7+8*9A-B$	$B-A98+7-6+5*43*21$
2968	04832	$-1*2*(3-4+5*6*-7-89*(A+B))$	$-BA+98*7*6+54-32*-1$
2969	04833	$1-234*-5*-6-(7+89)*-AB$	$BA9+8+7*6-5*-432*1$
296A	04834	$1+2345-6-78-9*A*-B$	$-B+A9-(8+7+654)*(-3-2)+1$
296B	04835	$12-(-3456+7-(-8-9*A*B))$	$-BA+9+876*(5-4+3)*(2-1)$
2970	04836	$1-(2-3*(4+5))*(67+89)+AB$	$B-(A-98*7*6)-(5-(-4-3))-21$
2971	04837	$1-23+4-5*-678+9*A-B$	$B-(-A-9)-(-8+7-6-54*-3*-21)$
2972	04838	$1+2+3456+7-8+9*-A*B$	$-BA-9*-8*7-6*(-543+21)$
2973	04839	$1-2*345*-6-(789-AB)$	$B+A+9+8+7*(6+5-4)^3*2-1$
2974	04840	$-1-2+3456-7-8*(-9+AB)$	$-B*-A*(-98+76+54-3*-2*1)$
2975	04841	$-1-2+3456-789+AB$	$-BA-9+(-876-5)*-4+3+2-1$
2976	04842	$-1*(2-3456+789-AB)$	$BA+9-87-6+54*-3*-21$
2977	04843	$-1+2345-67-8+9*A*B$	$-B-A*9-8*(7-6-(5+432))*1$
2978	04844	$12*(345-6-7-89-A-B)$	$-B+A9+87+6*543-2-1$
2979	04845	$-1+2+3456-789+AB$	$B+A+9*8*(7*6+5*4+3+2)^1$
297A	04846	$12+34-5*-678-9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*5*(4*3)^2+1$
297B	04847	$1+2-(-3456+789-AB)$	$B+A9+8*7-6*-543+21$
2980	04848	$123+4-5*-678-9A+B$	$B+A*-9-8*7*65-(-432-1)$
2981	04849	$12+3456+7-8-9*-A*-B$	$-B-A-9+87-6*(-543-21)$
2982	04850	$1-(-2+34-5*678-9A)-B$	$B-A9-8-7+(6+5)*(-4+321)$
2983	04851	$-1-2+3+(-4+5+6)*-7*(8-9A+B)$	$BA-9+8-76+54*-3*-21$
2984	04852	$-1+234+5-(6*7*-89-A*B)$	$-B-A9-8*(-765-(-4-321))$
2985	04853	$1+2+34-5*-678+9+A+B$	$-BA-9*(-8-7)*(6+5+4-3+21)$
2986	04854	$-1+2-(34-56*78)+9*-AB$	$BA9-87*6*-5-43*(-2+1)$
2987	04855	$-1-23-(4+5*-678)-(-9A+B)$	$BA+9+8*-7*(-6-(-5-4))*(-3-21)$
2988	04856	$1+23-4*(-5+67-89A-B)$	$BA9-8+76*-5*(-4-3)+2-1$
2989	04857	$-1-(23-4)-(-5*-678+9A*-B)$	$BA+98*7*6-5+4*-32*1$
298A	04858	$12-(-3456+789-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8-7*-6+54*3*21$
298B	04859	$-12-3-4-5*(6-(789-AB))$	$B+A+(-9+8+7*6)*(-5+4^3)*2^1$
2990	04860	$-1+2345-(6+7-(-8*-9A-B))$	$BA9-8+76-5*(-432+1)$
2991	04861	$12-34+5*678+9A-B$	$B+A-9*8-7+6+(5*4-3)^(2+1)$
2992	04862	$-1-2+(-3-4)*(-567+89+A-B)$	$BA-9+8*7*(65+4+3)+21$
2993	04863	$-1-(-2+34)-(-5*-678+9-AB)$	$B-(-A-98*-7*-6)+5*(-4+3)-21$
2994	04864	$-12+3456+7-8*9A-B$	$BA+98-7*(-654+321)$
2995	04865	$12+3456+7+8-9*A*B$	$BA9-8-(-76-5*-432*-1)$
2996	04866	$-1+2*34*56+7*(-8*-9-AB)$	$BA9+8*76+54*32+1$
2997	04867	$-1+2+3+4+5*678-9*-A-B$	$-B-A-(9-87+6+54*3*-21)$
2998	04868	$123-(4-5*(-6-7))*8*-9-(A+B)$	$B-A+9+8-7*65*(-4-3-2)-1$
2999	04869	$-1-2+3*(456+789-AB)$	$B+A9-8*7*(-65-4-3)+21$
299A	04870	$1-(-2-3456)-(-78*-9+AB)$	$BA9-8+76+5*(432+1)$
299B	04871	$-12-3-4*(56-7-(89A+B))$	$BA9-(-8+7)-65*(-4-32+1)$
29A0	04872	$-12*-3*(45+67-8-9-A+B)$	$B-A98-7*-6-5*43*-21$
29A1	04873	$1*2*(3+4)^(5+6-7)+8*9+A-B$	$-B*(A+987-654-32)*-1$
29A2	04874	$1-(-2345-6-(-7+8*9A)+B)$	$B-A+9+8*(7-6+5-432)*-1$
29A3	04875	$-1+2-(-345+6*-7*89)-(A+B)$	$BA-9+87+654*(3+2)-1$
29A4	04876	$12-(34-5*678+9)+AB$	$BA+98-(7-6*543+2)+1$
29A5	04877	$-123-(4+5-6+7*8*9*-A)+B$	$BA9+87-(6*5*43*-2-1)$
29A6	04878	$12-(-3456+7)-(-8*9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-98-7)-6*(-543-21)$
29A7	04879	$-1-2+34+5+6*78*9-AB$	$BA9+87-(6+5*-432+1)$
29A8	04880	$1*(-2-3)*(4-567+8+9*(-A-B))$	$BA9+8+76+5*432-1$
29A9	04881	$-12+345-6*-7*-89*(A-B)$	$B+A*98*7*(65-(-4-321))$
29AA	04882	$-1+2-3+4-5*(6-789+AB)$	$B-(-A9-87)-6*(-543-2)+1$
29AB	04883	$-1-2+3456-7-8*9A+B$	$-B+A9+8*7*65-4+321$
29B0	04884	$-1-(234+567*-8-9*-AB)$	$B*(-A-9+8+76+54+3)*(2+1)$
29B1	04885	$-1-23*4+56*-7*-8-9A*-B$	$-BA-9*8*(7-65)+4*3-21$
29B2	04886	$-1-(-2345-678-(-9+A-B))$	$B-A+98-7+6*(543+21)$
29B3	04887	$1+2345+678+(-9+A)*-B$	$B+A-9+8*76*5+43*21$
29B4	04888	$-12+3456+7*(8-9-AB)$	$-BA9+8-7*-6*(5-4*-32)-1$
29B5	04889	$-12-3+4-5*-678-9+AB$	$BA-(-98-7)-(-6*543-2*-1)$
29B6	04890	$-1-2+34*(56+78)-9AB$	$B-A-9+8+76+54*3*21$
29B7	04891	$-12+3*4+56*78+9*-AB$	$B+A-9+87+6*(543+21)$
29B8	04892	$-12+34-5*(-678+9)+AB$	$BA9-(-87-6-5*-432*-1)$
29B9	04893	$-1+2345-6-78*-9+AB$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*(5*4*3-2)^1$
29BA	04894	$12-34+5*678+9+AB$	$B+A9+87-(6*-543-21)$
29BB	04895	$12+3*-4+56*78+9*-AB$	$-B*(-A9+87+(6+54)*3*-2+1)$
2A00	04896	$1+2-34*(-56-78)-9AB$	$BA-98+(-76-5)*-43+21$
2A01	04897	$1+2+3+4-5*-678+9A-B$	$B-A-9*8*(7+6-5-43-21)$
2A02	04898	$1*(2-3)*(4-5*678-(-9+AB))$	$B-A98+7*-65*-4*3-21$
2A03	04899	$1-2+3456+7+8*-9A+B$	$-BA-9+8+76*(5+43)+2*1$
2A04	04900	$12*(34-5+67+89+AB)$	$-BA-(-9+8-76*(5+43))-(-2+1)$
2A05	04901	$123+456*7+89+AB$	$-B-A98+7*654-3-21$
2A06	04902	$12+3456+78*-9-A*B$	$BA-(-98-7-6*(543+2))-1$
2A07	04903	$-1+2-(-3456+7*(-8+9+AB))$	$-B-A98-7*-65*-4*-3+2*1$
2A08	04904	$-1+2345+678-(-9-(A-B))$	$BA+98+7-6*(-543-2)+1$
2A09	04905	$-1+2345+678-9*(A-B)$	$BA9-87*-6*5+43*2*1$
2A0A	04906	$-1+2345+678+9-A+B$	$B+A-(-98+7)+6*(543+21)$
2A0B	04907	$1*2345+678+9-(A-B)$	$B-A+9+87-6+54*-3*-21$
2A10	04908	$-1+2345+678-9+A+B$	$-B+A-(9+8*7*6*-5-4*321)$
2A11	04909	$1+2345+678-(-9+A)*-B$	$B+A+9+8-7*6+(5+4*3)^(2+1)$
2A12	04910	$1+2345-(-678+9-A)+B$	$B-A+98*7*6+(5-4)*32-1$
2A13	04911	$1+23-4-5*-678-(-9A+B)$	$-BA+987+6*(5-432)*-1$
2A14	04912	$1-23+456*-7+8*-9*-AB$	$BA-9*8*7*6-54*-3*21$
2A15	04913	$-12+34+5*678+9A-B$	$-B-A+98*-7*-6-(-54+3-2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2A16	04914	$-1 * (-2-34) * (5+6+7-8+9A-B)$	$B-A98-7*-654-(32-1)$
2A17	04915	$123+4 * (-56-(7-89A+B))$	$-BA+9+8-7*-6*-5*4*-3*2*1$
2A18	04916	$12+3456-7*(-8-(-9-AB))$	$-B-A9-8*(-765-4+321)$
2A19	04917	$1+2345+6-7-8*(9-AB)$	$-B*(A98-765-4*3*2)*-1$
2A1A	04918	$1+2345-6-(-789+AB)$	$B+A+9*8*7*6+5*4*3-2*1$
2A1B	04919	$-123-4-5-6*78*-9+AB$	$-B+A-(98*7*-6-(-5+43+2))*1$
2A20	04920	$-1*-234*(5-(6+7+8-(9A-B)))$	$-B-A98+7*654+3*(-2-1)$
2A21	04921	$-1-2*-3-45+6*78*9-(A-B)$	$-BA9+8*(7+6)*54-(-3+21)$
2A22	04922	$-1+2345-67-89*-A+B$	$BA-9-8+765*4+321$
2A23	04923	$-1-2*3*-45*-6+7*-8*(9-AB)$	$-BA+9+8*(765-(-4+321))$
2A24	04924	$1-23-(-456+78)*9*(-A+B)$	$B+A+98*-7*-6+5+43-21$
2A25	04925	$-12+34+5*678-(-9-A*B)$	$-B+A9-(-8+7)+6-54*3*-21$
2A26	04926	$-1+2345+678+9+A+B$	$-B+A-98+76*(5+43)+2+1$
2A27	04927	$1*2345+678-(-9-A)+B$	$B-A-9-(876*-5-43*-21)$
2A28	04928	$1+2345+678-(-9-A)+B$	$-B+A-98*7*-6+5+43+2-1$
2A29	04929	$-1*(-2345-6-(789-AB))$	$-BA9-8*7*(654-3+21)$
2A2A	04930	$1+2345+6+789-AB$	$B+A-9-8-7*(-6-5)*4*3-2*1$
2A2B	04931	$-1+23-4+5*678+9A+B$	$-B-A98+7*654-(-3+2-1)$
2A30	04932	$-1-2-3+456*7-8*-9*-AB$	$B+A9-(8*(7-6)+54*-3*21)$
2A31	04933	$-1-23-4-567*-8-9AB$	$BA-98*7*-6-5-43-21$
2A32	04934	$1*(-2*-3*(4+5)+6*7)/8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6-5*4-3+2)*1$
2A33	04935	$1-23-4-567*-8-9AB$	$-B-(-A-9+8*7*-65-(432+1))$
2A34	04936	$1*2+3*(-4-5*-6*7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A98-7*(-654-3+2)*1$
2A35	04937	$-1+2345+6-7+8+9*A*B$	$-B+A+9*-8*-76+543*2*-1$
2A36	04938	$1+23-4-(56-78)*9*(A+B)$	$BA-(9-(8+765*4))+321$
2A37	04939	$1-(-2345+6-789-A*-B)$	$-B-A+98+(76+5)*43-2+1$
2A38	04940	$1+2*-3*-456-78+9*AB$	$BA-(-9+8-765*4-321)$
2A39	04941	$1-2+3+5*678-9+AB$	$-BA9+8*-76+5+4321$
2A3A	04942	$-1+23-4-5*-678+9+AB$	$BA+9-(-8+76)*-54-321$
2A3B	04943	$-1-2345-(-6-7*89A)-B$	$-BA9-87*-65-43*21$
2A40	04944	$1234-5-6*7*-8*9-AB$	$-B+A-(-98-7)*(-6-5+43)+21$
2A41	04945	$1*(2-34-5)*(-6*7+8*-9+A-B)$	$B-A98-7*-654+3*-2*1$
2A42	04946	$-12+3456-7*89-AB$	$BA9-8+7+65*(-4-32)*-1$
2A43	04947	$12-3-4+5*(6+789-AB)$	$-BA+98*-7*-6-54*-3+21$
2A44	04948	$-123-4-(-56*7*8-9AB)$	$B-(A98-7*654+3*(2-1))$
2A45	04949	$12-3-4-5+6*78*9-A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7+6*5)*4*3*(2-1)$
2A46	04950	$1*(2-(-3-4+56-7))*8-9A+B$	$-BA9+876*5-(4-321)$
2A47	04951	$-12-3-(4-5+6*78*9-A)-B$	$B-A98-7*-654-3+2+1$
2A48	04952	$-1-23*4*(-56+7)+8-9AB$	$BA9+8*-7*(6-54)-3*(2+1)$
2A49	04953	$1*2345+67+8*9A-B$	$-B+A+98-7*(-65-432)+1$
2A4A	04954	$-12-3-(-456+78)*9-(-A-B)$	$BA9-87*-6*5-4*-32-1$
2A4B	04955	$-1+2-34-56*7*-8-9A*-B$	$-B+A9-8+(-76-5)*43*(-2+1)$
2A50	04956	$12*(3+4+5-678+9A*B)$	$-B-A+9*87-6*(5+4)*-3*2*1$
2A51	04957	$1-23+4*(-5+678)+9*AB$	$-B-A98+7*654+3+21$
2A52	04958	$123-4+5*-678*(9-A)+B$	$-BA9+876*5+4+321$
2A53	04959	$12-34+5*(6-7-(-8-9*-A*-B))$	$-B+A+98-7*(-65-432-1)$
2A54	04960	$1+2345+6-78*(9-A)*B$	$BA-98*7*-6-5-43-2*-1$
2A55	04961	$-1*(-2-345-(67-89-A))*B$	$B*(-A-9+8)*(-76-5+43+2+1)$
2A56	04962	$1-2*-3*-456-7*(-89A+B)$	$B-A-(-9-8*(7+6*(54-32*-1)))$
2A57	04963	$1+2+3456-7*89-AB$	$B+A+9*-8*(-7*-6*-5+4)/3-2*1$
2A58	04964	$-1+2+3456-7+8*(-9A+B)$	$B+A-9-8*(7-6-5*4+3+2)*1$
2A59	04965	$1-2-3+4+567*8-9AB$	$-B+A+9*(-87-65-4)*-3+2*-1$
2A5A	04966	$1+2345-(-6*7+8-9*A*B)$	$BA-98-(7+6)*5*(-43-21)$
2A5B	04967	$1-(-2-3)-4-567*-8-9AB$	$-B-A98-7*-654+32*1$
2A60	04968	$-1*-23*4*(5-6+7*8-9)*(-A+B)$	$BA+9*(87-6)*5+4+321$
2A61	04969	$1+234-5*-678-(9+AB)$	$B-A-9*-8*(7-6)*54+3+2*1$
2A62	04970	$1234-56*(-7-8-(-9-A))*-B$	$-BA+987-6*(-5-432)-1$
2A63	04971	$12-3-4-5-6*-78*9-A+B$	$-B-(A+9)+8-(-7-6)*54*3*2+1$
2A64	04972	$12-(3+4)-(567*-8+9AB)$	$B*(-A9-876-5+4*321)$
2A65	04973	$-1-2+3*(-45-6*7)*(-8-9)+AB$	$BA9+87-65*(-4-(32-1))$
2A66	04974	$-1+2345+67+8*9A+B$	$B+A9-(8*7*6-54*3*21)$
2A67	04975	$-1+2-3+4+5+6*78*9*(-A+B)$	$B-A98+7*(654+3)-(-2-1)$
2A68	04976	$1*2345+678+9*A-B$	$BA9+8-765*(-4+3+2*-1)$
2A69	04977	$1*(-2+3)*(45-(-67-89))*(A+B)$	$B+A*(-9+876)+5-4321$
2A70	04978	$-1+2+3456+7-8*(9A-B)$	$BA-9+8-7*(-65-432*1)$
2A71	04979	$-1-234+5+6*-7*(-8-9A)+B$	$-B+A*987-6*-5*4*3*-21$
2A72	04980	$1-2+3456+7*-89+A*-B$	$-B-A9*-8+7-65*-43+21$
2A73	04981	$123-4*5+6*-7*(-8-9A+B)$	$-BA9+87*(6+54-3-2)-1$
2A74	04982	$123+4+56*(78-(9+A))-B$	$-BA-9-876+5*-43*-21$
2A75	04983	$1*(23-4-5*(6-78))*(9-A)*-B$	$-B*(-A98+765-4-3+21)$
2A76	04984	$-12*(345+6-(7-(8-9)-AB))$	$-B+A-98*(7+6-5-43)-2-1$
2A77	04985	$-12+3456-78*9-(A-B)$	$BA-9+8+7*(65+432+1)$
2A78	04986	$1-2*-3*(-4+567)+89+A*B$	$B+A9+8-7*(-65-432)+1$
2A79	04987	$-1-23*-4+5*(-6-(-789+AB))$	$-BA9+8-7*(-654-(3+21))$
2A80	04988	$1-23-4-5-6-7*8*-9*A-B$	$B+A-9*8+7*6*5*4*3*2-1$
2A81	04989	$1+23-4-567*-8-9AB$	$B-A98+7*654+32*1$
2A82	04990	$1-2+3+4-5+6*-78*-9+A+B$	$B+A-98*7*-6-5-43*-2*1$
2A83	04991	$12+3456+78*-9-A-B$	$B+A+9*8*(7*6+(5+4)*3)+2*1$
2A84	04992	$-1+2345+6+7-89*-A-B$	$-B+A-9*(-87-65-4)*3+21$
2A85	04993	$-1+2+34*56-(7+89)*(-A-B)$	$-B-A9-876+5*43*21$
2A86	04994	$1+2345+6-(-7+89-A)-B$	$-B+A-9*(8+7)*(-6-(5+43)+21)$
2A87	04995	$-1*-23*(4-5-(67+89))*(A-B)$	$B+A+98*7*6+(-54-32)*-1$
2A88	04996	$-1-2+3456+78*-9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9*-8+7*654-321$
2A89	04997	$-1-(-2345-678+9)-A*-B$	$-B+A9+87-6*(-543-21)$
2A90	04998	$12*(345-(6+7)-8-9A+B)$	$B+A+9+8*(7-6+5*4-3-2)*1$
2A91	04999	$1-(-2345-678-9*A-B)$	$-BA-9-87*(-6+5-43+2*1)$
2A92	05000	$-1-(-234+5*-678)-(9A-B)$	$B+A-(-9+876*(-5+4-3)+2*-1)$
2A93	05001	$12-3-4-56*7*-8-9A*-B$	$-B+A9+8-(-7+6-54)*-3*-21$
2A94	05002	$-1-2+34+567*8-9AB$	$BA9-8-7*(-654+321)$
2A95	05003	$1*-2+34-567*-8-9AB$	$BA9+8*7+65*(-4-32)*-1$
2A96	05004	$1-(-2345+6)-(-7+89*-A-B)$	$-B-A98-7*-654-3*-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2A91	05005	1+2345+678+9A-B	-B*(-A+987-654-3*2)*-1
2A92	05006	1+23-(-4-5-6*(78-9)*A)-B	-B+A9+8*(76+54+321)
2A93	05007	1234+5*-67*-8-(-9-A)*-B	-BA9+8*(-7+65)*4*3*(2-1)
2A94	05008	1+234+5*678+9A*-B	BA-98*-7*6*(5-4)-3*-2*-1
2A95	05009	-1-2*3+4*-56*(7-(-89+AB))	B+A*-9*8*-7+6+5-(-43-2)*-1
2A96	05010	-1*-2*3*(-45+6-7*(-89-A-B))	B+A+9-8*(7-6-5^4+3/2)^1
2A97	05011	12+3456-78*9+A-B	-BA+98+76*(5+43)-2-1
2A98	05012	12*(-3-456+789+A*-B)	BA-9+87+6*(543+21)
2A99	05013	12+3456+78*-9-(A-B)	BA9-8*-76*5+4*-3*21
2A9A	05014	-12+3456+7*(8+9-AB)	-BA98-7*6*(5+432*-1)
2A9B	05015	-1+2345+678+9A*B	B-A9-876+5*-43*-21
2AA0	05016	1*(2-3)*(-45-67)*(-8*9+A*B)	-B*(-A+9-8+7-6-(-5-(4-321)))
2AA1	05017	12+34-56+7*8*9*A-B	BA9-8*-7*(65+4+3-21)
2AA2	05018	-1+2345-(-678+9-AB)	BA+98*-7*-6+5+4-(-3-2)*-1
2AA3	05019	12-(-345-6*-7*-89+A*-B)	B-(-A9-87-6*(543+21))
2AA4	05020	1-(-2345-(678-9))+AB	-B-A+9*-8*(7-65)-(-4-3-2)*1
2AA5	05021	-1+2345-6-78+9*AB	BA-9*-87+65*43+21
2AA6	05022	1*23*(45-6+7-8+9+AB)	B-A*-9*8-7*(6-5-432)*1
2AA7	05023	1+2345-(6+78-9*AB)	BA9-8+7+65*(4+32+1)
2AA8	05024	1+2+3456+7*(-8-9A+B)	B-A+9*(8+76)*5+432-1
2AA9	05025	-1+2345+678+9A+B	B+A+9+8^7(7-6)*5^4-3-2^1
2AAA	05026	-1*(-2345-678-9A-B)	B-(-A-9*8*(-7+65)-4+32+1)
2AAB	05027	1-(-2345-678)-(-9A-B)	-BA-9*87*-6-(-54+321)
2AB0	05028	1+2345-6+789-A-B	B+A+9+8^7(7-6)*5^4-3+2-1
2AB1	05029	1+2+345-6*-7*89+AB	-B+A98*7-65*(43+21)
2AB2	05030	-1+2+34+5*678+(-9-A)*-B	BA-(-9-87)+6*(543+21)
2AB3	05031	-1+2345-6*-7*-8+9AB	BA+9-8*(-7+6-(-5+432)*1)
2AB4	05032	-123-45*(-6-78)-9*(A-B)	-B+A*98-765*-4-321
2AB5	05033	12-3456-78*-9A-B	-B-A*-9*-8*-7-(6-5)*4*(-3+2)*1
2AB6	05034	1*2345-(-6+78-9*AB)	B-A9+(-87-65-4)*(-3-21)
2AB7	05035	-1+2-(-34-56*7*8-9A*B)	BA-98*7*-6-(5-43+21)
2AB8	05036	-1+2345+678+9+AB	-B+A9-(87*-6*5+4*-321)
2AB9	05037	1-2-(-345-6+7-8*9A)*B	B+A9-(-87+6-54*-3*-21)
2ABA	05038	1-(-2345-(678+9)-AB)	BA+9*-8*(-7-6-5-43+2-1)
2ABB	05039	-1*(-2345-(6+789-A-B))	BA9+8+7-65*(-4-(32+1))
2B00	05040	1+2345-(-6-789-(A-B))	-BA9-8-7*(-654-32)-1
2B01	05041	1+2*3*4*5*-6*-7*(8-9)*(A-B)	-BA+9+87+(-6-5)*(-4-321)
2B02	05042	-1+2-(-34-5-6)*(78+9)-A*B	BA-9(8-7*(654+32)-1)
2B03	05043	1-(-2+3)-(-45*-67-8*(9A-B))	B-A-9+8-76*(-5-43)+2+1
2B04	05044	-1+2*34-567*-8-9AB	-B+A9-8*7*-65-432*-1
2B05	05045	1+2345-6*-7+89*A+B	-BA-98-76*-54-321
2B06	05046	-1+2345-(6-789)+A-B	B+A*-9*-8*7+6+54-3*21
2B07	05047	-1*(-2345+6-789-A+B)	B+A+(-9-8*-7*6*5+4)*3+2-1
2B08	05048	-1+2345-6+789-(A-B)	-BA9-8+7*(654+32+1)
2B09	05049	-1*(-2345+6-789+A-B)	-B*(-A-987-(-654+3)+21)
2B0A	05050	1+2345-(6-789+A)+B	B+A+9+8*(7-6+5^4+3/2)^1
2B0B	05051	-1+2345+67-8*(-9A-B)	B-A-9*8*(7-65)+4+3+2+1
2B10	05052	-1+2*345*-6-(-78+9)*AB	-B-A*98-7*(-654+32+1)
2B11	05053	1234-5+67*(8+9+A+B)	-B-A*-9*8*7-65+43*2-1
2B12	05054	123-4-5*-678+9A-B	B-A*-98-765*-4-321
2B13	05055	12-3456-78*-9A+B	-B+A98+76*(-5+4)*(-32-1)
2B14	05056	123+4+5*678-(9+A*-B)	B+A-9*8-7-6+5*4^3(3+2^1)
2B15	05057	-1+2345-6+7*-8+9*AB	BA+98-7-(-6-54*-3*-21)
2B16	05058	-1+2345+6-(-789-A+B)	B+A9+87*6*5*4*-321
2B17	05059	-1*(-2345-67+89*-A+B)	BA-(-98-7+6+54*3*21)
2B18	05060	1*-2*(3*(-4-567)-(-8+9A+B))	B*(-A9-87-(-65-432-1))
2B19	05061	1+2345+6-789*(A-B)	B+A+9-8+7*6*5*4*3*2-1
2B1A	05062	1-(-2345-6)-(-789-(A+B))	B+A+9*87*6-54-321
2B1B	05063	1+2345-6+7+8*(9+AB)	B+A+9-8+7*6*5*4*3*2+1
2B20	05064	-1*2*3*4*(-5+6)*(-78-9-A*B)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5*4*3+2+1
2B21	05065	-1+2*34*56-78+9-AB	B+A+(9*8*7*6*5*4*3)/(2+1)
2B22	05066	123-4+5*678-(-9+A*-B)	B-A+9+8*(765+4-321)
2B23	05067	-1-2-(-3456-7*-89-(A-B))	B+A-9*8-7+6+5*4^3(3+2)-1
2B24	05068	-1+2345-6-(-789-A-B)	B+A+987+6*(-5+432-1)
2B25	05069	-1-2-345-(-67*8*9+AB)	B+A*-98-7-(6-5*43)*21
2B26	05070	1+2*(3+4)+5+(-6-7*-8)*(-9*-A+B)	B+A+9+8*7*6*(5+4+3+2+1)
2B27	05071	1-(-23+45*67)+8*(9A-B)	B+A*9*8+765*4-3-(-2-1)
2B28	05072	1-23+4+567*8-9A*B	BA+98*7*6+5+(-43-2)*-1
2B29	05073	1+2+3456-7*89-(A+B)	BA9+8*7*(-6+54+3-2+1)
2B2A	05074	-12+3*45*(-67-8-(-9-A*B))	BA+98*7*6+54-3-2+1
2B2B	05075	1-234-(567*-8-9*-A*B)	B-(-A9+876*5)-43*-21
2B30	05076	1+2-3+4*(-56-78+9AB)	B+A-9-8*(7-6-5^4-3^2)^1
2B31	05077	-1*(23-4*(5-(6-7+8-9A)))*B)	BA+9-8*-7*65+432*1
2B32	05078	-12+3456+7*-89-A+B	-BA-98*(7-6-(5-43+2))*-1
2B33	05079	1-2-(-3-4)-5+6*7*8*9-A*-B	B+A+9+8+7*6*5*4*3*2+1
2B34	05080	-1+2345+67-89*-A+B	BA9+8*7+65*(4+32+1)
2B35	05081	1*2345-(-6-(789+A))+B	B+A-9-8-7*6*5*4^3(3+2)-1
2B36	05082	-1*2*-3*(-4+5+6)*(-7-8-(9-AB))	-B*(-A-(-9-(-8+765-432)))*-1
2B37	05083	-1+2-3*4+567*8-9A*B	BA-98*7*(-6-(-543+2))^1
2B38	05084	12+3456+7*-89-A-B	-B+A*98+7+65*43-(-2+1)
2B39	05085	123-45+6*78*9A-B	BA+9*-87*-6-(-5-432)*-1
2B3A	05086	1-2-3-(4+5)+6*-78*-9+AB	-B+A9+8*(7-(6-5)+432+1)
2B3B	05087	-1+23+45*(67-8)-9A*-B	B-(-A+9*8*(7-65))-(-4+3-21)
2B40	05088	1*(2-(-3+4)-5)*(-6-(7+89A)+B)	BA9+8+7-6*-5*4*(3+21)
2B41	05089	1-2+3456+78*(-9-A+B)	B+A+9-8*7-6+5*4^3(3+2)+1
2B42	05090	-1+23*-4*(-56+7)-(89A+B)	B-A*-9+(-876-5)*-4+3-2*1
2B43	05091	1*2+3*(-4^5+6)*(-7-8)/9A-B	B+A+(-9/-8+7)*(6+5^4-3*2-1)
2B44	05092	-1+2+3456-7*-89*(A-B)	B+A-9+8*(7-6+5^4+3^2)^1
2B45	05093	-1+2+3456-7*89-A+B	-B*(-A+9-(-8+765-432)+1)
2B46	05094	-1*(2+3+(4+56)*(-78+9A)+B)	-BA-98+7*(-6+543)-(2+1)
2B47	05095	-1-(-234-5*678)-(-9+A)-B	BA+98+7*(-65-432)*-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
2B48	05096	$-1-234+5*(678+9A+B)$	$B-A+987+65*(43-2-1)$
2B49	05097	$-1+234-5*-678-9-(-A+B)$	$B+A-9+8-7*6+5*4*(3+2)-1$
2B4A	05098	$-1+2345-6-7-8+9*AB$	$-BA-98+7*(-6+543)+2-1$
2B4B	05099	$-1+2+3456+7*(-89-A+B)$	$B-A*(-98+7*-6*5)-4*-321$
2B50	05100	$1+2345-6-7-8-9*-AB$	$-BA-98-7*(6-543)-(-2-1)$
2B51	05101	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7*8*-9*-A-B$	$BA-9-8*(-7-6-(-5+432)+1)$
2B52	05102	$-1+2345+6*7-8*(-9-AB)$	$-B-A9-(8+7*-6*-5*(-4+3)*21)$
2B53	05103	$1+234-56*-78+9A*B$	$B-A*-9*8*7-(6-5)*(-43-2)-1$
2B54	05104	$12+3456*(-7*-89-A)-B$	$B*(-A9-87)*(65-4+3*-21)$
2B55	05105	$-12+345*-6*-7-89AB$	$B-A+98*(-7+65-43+21)$
2B56	05106	$(-1+2*3)*4^5-6-7^A(-8+9)+A-B$	$BA-9*-8*(-7+65)-43-21$
2B57	05107	$123-4-5*(-6-789+AB)$	$-B+A+98+(-7-6)*-54*3*2*1$
2B58	05108	$-12-(-34+56*-78+9*A*B)$	$-B-A9-8*(76-(543-21))$
2B59	05109	$1234-5*-6*7*8-9A+B$	$-BA9-(8-7*-65-4321)$
2B5A	05110	$-12*(3-45-(67+89+AB))$	$-BA+98*-7*-6+5*(43+21)$
2B5B	05111	$-1-(-23+4+5+6*(-7*8*9-A-B))$	$-BA9+87*5-432*-1$
2B60	05112	$1*2*3*4*(5-6+78-9+AB)$	$-BA*-9*(-8-76+54+32*1)$
2B61	05113	$-1+2+3456+7*-89-(-A-B)$	$-B+A-9*8*7*-6+5+4-321$
2B62	05114	$-12-3*-45-(6*(-78+9)*A+B)$	$BA9+8*-7*-6+5*(432-1)$
2B63	05115	$1234-5*6*7*-8+9-A*B$	$-B*(-A-(9+876-543)+21)$
2B64	05116	$-1+2+3*(-45+6+7-89-A)*-B$	$B+A+9+8-7*6+5*4*(3+2+1)$
2B65	05117	$-1+234-5*-678+9-A+B$	$B+A+9+8-7*6+5*4*(3+2)+1$
2B66	05118	$1-2-345*6*-7-89AB$	$B-A+(9+8)*-7*(-6+5-4-32)*1$
2B67	05119	$12+345-6*7*(8-9)*-A*-B$	$BA+9-87*5(5-4+3*-2+1)$
2B68	05120	$-1+2345-67-(-89A+B)$	$-BA+9-87*(-65+43-21)$
2B69	05121	$-1*(-2345+67-89A+B)$	$-B+A*98*(7-(6-5))+4*-321$
2B6A	05122	$1+2345-67-(-89A+B)$	$B+A+9/8*7*6^5/4/3-2*1$
2B6B	05123	$1-2-345+6*7*(-8+9*A-B)$	$-B+A-9-876-5*43*-21$
2B70	05124	$12*3*(45-67-(-8-9-AB))$	$B+A+9*(87+6+5-4+321)$
2B71	05125	$-12-3+45*6*7-8*-9A+B$	$-BA9+8-7*6^5+4321$
2B72	05126	$-1+2345+6-7+8-9*-AB$	$-B*(A-(987-654)-3+2*-1)$
2B73	05127	$-12-34-(567-89A)*B$	$B+A+9/8*7*6^5/4/3+2+1$
2B74	05128	$1-2-(-3456-78*-9)+AB$	$BA-9*8*(7-65)-(43+2)-1$
2B75	05129	$-1-23+456*(7-8+9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5*4*(3+2+1)$
2B76	05130	$123-4-5-6*7*8*-9*(-A+B)$	$B-A*-98+7-65*-43+21$
2B77	05131	$12+34-5-6*-7*(-8+9A+B)$	$B+A-9+8^A(7-6)*5*4^3*2-1$
2B78	05132	$123-4-(567*8+9AB)$	$B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4*3*2-1$
2B79	05133	$1-234-5*6*7*(89-AB)$	$B+A+987-(6*(-5-432)+1)$
2B7A	05134	$1+2*-34+56*7*8-9*AB$	$B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4*3*2+1$
2B7B	05135	$-12-(3-45)-(-6*-7*8*9-AB)$	$-B+A-(9-8+7)*-6*(5-43*-2*1)$
2B80	05136	$12+3+4+5-6*7*8*-9+AB$	$B+A-9*8*7-6+5^4*3^2/1$
2B81	05137	$1-23+45*6*7-8*(9-AB)$	$-B+A-9-87-(6+54)*-3*21$
2B82	05138	$12+3456+7+8*9*-A+B$	$B+A-9-8+7+6+5*4*(3+2)+1$
2B83	05139	$(1^2+3+4^5)*(6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$BA9*(8-7+6-5-4+3+2)*1$
2B84	05140	$-1+2345+6+7+8+9*AB$	$-BA-98+76*5*4*3-2*1$
2B85	05141	$-1-23-45*-67-(8-9*-A*-B)$	$-B-(-A-9+876+5*43*-21)$
2B86	05142	$-1+2345-67+89A+B$	$B-(-A-(98+7))-6*-5*(-4-3)*-21$
2B87	05143	$-1*(-2345+67-89A-B)$	$B+A+9-8+7-6+5*4*(3+2+1)$
2B88	05144	$1+2345-67-(-89A-B)$	$B+A9*-87-6*5*432*-1$
2B89	05145	$-1+23-4-56*-7*8+9AB$	$-B+A-9-(87+654)*(-3*2+1)$
2B8A	05146	$-1+2*-34*-56-7-89-A-B$	$-BA-98*-7+6*(543-21)$
2B8B	05147	$-1*2-3*(4^5+6)*(-7-8)/9+A-B$	$B-(-A+98)+7*(6-(-543+21))$
2B8C	05148	$12+34+56*7*8-9A*B$	$B*(A-9*87+654+321)$
2B8D	05149	$-12-(-34+56*-7*8-9AB)$	$-B+A9*(87-6-5-43-(2-1))$
2B8E	05150	$1^2-3*(4^5+6)*(-7-8)/9+A-B$	$-B+A98+7*(-6+54+321)$
2B8F	05151	$-1+2345-(67+8+9A*B)$	$-BA-9-8-76*(-54+3*2-1)$
2B90	05152	$-1-(-2345-6-(-78-9A*-B))$	$B+A-9+8+7+6+5*4*(3+2)-1$
2B91	05153	$1+2345-67-8+9A*B$	$B+A9*-8+7*-6*(5-4*-32*-1)$
2B92	05154	$1+2345+6-(78-9A*B)$	$-BA-98-7*(6-543+21)$
2B93	05155	$12-34+(-567+89A)*B$	$-B-A9-8-76*-54-321$
2B94	05156	$-1+2+3+4+5+6*7*8*9+AB$	$B-A*87+(-6+5*43)*21$
2B95	05157	$-1-(-2345+6-789-A*B)$	$-B-A*(-9-876)-(-5+4321)$
2B96	05158	$-1*(-2345-6*-7-89A+B)$	$B+A+9-8*7+6^5*4/3/2*1$
2B97	05159	$1-23+4+(-567-89A)*-B$	$-BA-(-987-65*43+21)$
2B98	05160	$1+23-4-(5-(6-7))*8*(-9A+B)$	$-BA-9+8-76*-54-321$
2B99	05161	$1-2*-3*4*(-5-(-6-78)-9+AB)$	$-B+A9+8+(-76-5)*(-43-2)*1$
2BA0	05162	$1-2+3+4+5+6*-7*8+9AB$	$-BA+9-8-76*-54-321$
2BA1	05163	$-12-(345-6-7*8*(-9*-A+B))$	$B-(-A-(9-(876-5*-43*-21)))$
2BA2	05164	$-1-2-34*-5+6*-7*8*-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+7*6*5*4)*3*2+1$
2BA3	05165	$1-234*5-6*(-789-A-B)$	$-B+A-9*(-87-(654-321))$
2BA4	05166	$-12+3-4+(567-89A)*-B$	$-BA9+87-65*4*(3-21)$
2BA5	05167	$-1+2+(-34+5-6)*(-7-8+9)*(A+B)$	$-BA-98-7*(-6-543+2*1)$
2BA6	05168	$-1+234*-5-6*-789+AB$	$BA9-8+7+6*-54*3*(-2-1)$
2BA7	05169	$1+2345-6+7+8-9A*-B$	$B+A9-8-76*(-5-43)-2-1$
2BA8	05170	$1*2345+6+789+A*B$	$B*(-A98+765-(4-3)+2)*-1$
2BA9	05171	$1-(-2345-6-789-A*B)$	$B-A9*(-8-7+6-5-4+3-21)$
2BAB	05172	$1-2*3+(4-(-56+7))*8*(-8+9*A)+B$	$B-A+987-65*(-43+2)-1$
2BAC	05173	$1*-2345-6*(-78-9AB)$	$B-A+987+65*(43-2)*1$
2BAD	05174	$1-2345+6*(78+9AB)$	$B+A+9+8*(7+6+5^4+3+2)^A^1$
2BAE	05175	$1+(2*3-4-5)^6*7+8*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8*(76+543*(2-1))$
2BAF	05176	$-1*-2*(-3-4+5)*(-6-7-89A-B)$	$B-A+9*(87-(-6-(5+4)))+321)$
2BAB	05177	$12+34-56*-7*8+9AB$	$B-A9-(8-76*54+321)$
2BBB	05178	$-1+2345-6+789+AB$	$-BA+9+8-76*-54-321$
2BB4	05179	$-1+2345-6*7*(-89A-B)$	$-BA*9*8-(-7-6)*(-54+321)$
2BB5	05180	$12*(-3+4+5*67-(-89+AB))$	$B+A9-8*7*6*(5+4*3-2)*1$
2BB6	05181	$1+2345+6*-7-(-89A-B)$	$-B*(-A98+765)*(-4+3-2*-1)$
2BB7	05182	$1+2*34*-56+(7-8*-9A)*B$	$-BA+987*6+5*432*-1$
2BB8	05183	$1-2-3+(456-7)*8+9A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7*6+5*4*(3+2)-1$
2BB9	05184	$1*-2*3*(-4-5-678-9-A*-B)$	$BA-9+8+76*(5+43)-(-2-1)$
2BA0	05185	$-1234-56*-78+9*AB$	$-BA-(-9-8+76*(-5-43-(2+1)))$
2BA1	05186	$-1+2345-6-(7-89A)-B$	$-BA+987-65*-43-2*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3003	05187	$-1 * (-2345+6+7-89A+B)$	$-BA-98-(-765-4)*(3-2*-1)$
3004	05188	$1-(-2345+6+7-89A+B)$	$-BA-98*7*-6-(-5-(-4+321))$
3005	05189	$-12-3*-45*-6+(-7*-8-9)*AB$	$-B-A*(9-8*(7-6))-54-321)$
3006	05190	$-1+2345+6-(-789-AB)$	$BA-9-8+76*(5+43)+21$
3007	05191	$-1*(-2345-(6+789)-AB)$	$-B-(-A98+7)-(-6*(-5+432)+1)$
3008	05192	$1+2345+6+789+AB$	$-B*(A+9-8-(76-54+321))$
3009	05193	$1+2*3+45*(6+78)-(9+A)+B$	$B-A+9+8+76*54-321$
300A	05194	$-12*(-3-45-67-89-AB)$	$BA+987-6*(5-432)-1$
300B	05195	$1+234-5*(-678+9)+AB$	$B+A-9-8+7+6*5*4/3/2/1$
3010	05196	$123-45-6*-78*9+A*B$	$-B-(-A-9-8)+7*(-6+543-21)$
3011	05197	$-1+23-4-5*(-678-9*A+B)$	$BA-98*7*-6-(-54+3)*(2+1)$
3012	05198	$-1+2345+6-7+89A-B$	$-BA9-(8+76*5-4321)$
3013	05199	$-1*(-2345+6+7-89A+B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6*5*4/3/2/1$
3014	05200	$-1-2-345+6*7*8*-9*(A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6*5*4/3/2+1$
3015	05201	$12+3*4+5*(678+9*A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8)*-7*(-6+543-21)$
3016	05202	$1+2345-6+7+89A-B$	$B-A9*(-8-7*6+5)+432*-1$
3017	05203	$-1-(2+3)-(456-7)*-8-(-9A-B)$	$-B*(A-9-(876-543))-(-2+1))$
3018	05204	$1-2+3-(456-7)*-8-(9-AB)$	$B+A+(9-8-7-6-5*4*3)^2-1$
3019	05205	$12+3456+7*8*-9-AB$	$-BA-9+87*(-6+5+43+2)*1$
301A	05206	$1-(-2345-6+7)-(89A+A)*-B$	$-B+A98+7-6*(5-432)*1$
301B	05207	$1-234-(-5*(-6+789)-A)-B$	$-BA-98+76*(54-3)-21$
3020	05208	$-1+2345-6-7+89A+B$	$B-(-A+98-76*54+321)$
3021	05209	$1+2-3-4+567*8+9*-AB$	$-B+A+9*8*76-(-5-43*-21)$
3022	05210	$1+2345-6-7+89A+B$	$BA9-8*7*(-6-(5+43))^2+1$
3023	05211	$-1+23*4+5-6*78*-9+AB$	$B+A-9+8+7+6*5*4/3/2/1$
3024	05212	$-1+2345+6+7-(-89A+B)$	$B+A+9-8+7+6*5*4/3/2-1$
3025	05213	$-1-2*-3*(45-(-678+9)-AB)$	$-BA-987-(-6-5)*432*1$
3026	05214	$1-(-2345-6-7)+89A-B$	$-B*(-A-9-8*7-6+54-321)$
3027	05215	$12+3456-7*89-A*-B$	$B+A987-65*(-4-3)*-21$
3028	05216	$1+234-5*-678+9A-B$	$-B-A9-87*(65-43)*-2*1$
3029	05217	$123-45-(-6*-78*-9-AB)$	$B-A98-7*(-654-32)*1$
302A	05218	$-1+2345-(-6-7)-(-89-A)*B$	$B-A98+7*(654+32)+1$
302B	05219	$-1-2+3456+7*-89+AB$	$B+A+9+8-(-7+6*5+4)/-3*2-1$
3030	05220	$-1-(-2345-6+7-89A-B)$	$BA9+876-5*(4-321)$
3031	05221	$-1+2345+(-6+7)*89A+B$	$B-A+98*(-7+6)*(5-43+2-1)$
3032	05222	$-1+2345-(-6-7-89A-B)$	$-BA+9+876-(5+4)*-321$
3033	05223	$1-2-3*(-456-(789-A))-B$	$-BA+9+87*(-6+5)*(-43-2+1)$
3034	05224	$1+2345-6+7+89A+B$	$-BA9-8*76*(-5-4)+321$
3035	05225	$1+2+3456-(7*89-AB)$	$B*(A-(-987+654+3+2+1))$
3036	05226	$-1+2-3-45+6*7*(8+9A)-B$	$B+A*-98*(7-6)+5*-43*-21$
3037	05227	$12-(-34+5+6*(-7-8*(9A-B)))$	$-B-A9-8-76*5*-4*-3-21$
3038	05228	$1+23+(-45+6+7)*(-8+9-AB)$	$B+A+9+8+7+6*5*4/3/2-1$
3039	05229	$-1-2*-34*5+6*7*(8+9A-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7+6*5*4/3/2/1$
303A	05230	$1234+5*6+(-7-8-9)*-AB$	$B-A+9+(8-76)*-54-3-21$
303B	05231	$-1+2345-6-(-7+8+9A*-B)$	$BA+98*7*6+54*3+21$
3040	05232	$1-2+34-56*(-7+8*-9)-A-B$	$-BA9-8-7*-654+321$
3041	05233	$-1+2345-6-(-7-8)-9A*-B$	$-BA-(-9-8+7*(6-543)-2)+1$
3042	05234	$-1+2345+6+7+89A+B$	$-B-(-A98+7+65*(-43+2+1))$
3043	05235	$1*(2-(3+4))*(-56+789)*(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8-(-7-6)*(-54+321)$
3044	05236	$-123-45+6*7*(-8-(-9+AB))$	$B*(A+987-654-3*2+1)$
3045	05237	$-1-23*(-4-5-(67+89-(A-B)))$	$B+A-9-(-8*-7+6*5+4)/-3*2+1$
3046	05238	$1*23*(-4+5+67-(8+9)+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(7+6-5*4*3)-2*1$
3047	05239	$-12+34-567*-8+9*-AB$	$B-A*(-98+76)*-5*-4-(-3-21)$
3048	05240	$-1*-2*(345-(-678-9*AB))$	$-BA+9*8+76*(5+43+2+1)$
3049	05241	$-1+2345+6*7-(-89A+B)$	$-B+A9*-8-765+4321$
304A	05242	$-1*(-2345+6*-7-(89A-B))$	$B+A+9+(8*7+6*5*4/3)/2*1$
304B	05243	$-1*(-2+34-(-5-6))*7*(-8-9)-AB)$	$B+A+9+(-8*-7-6*5*4/3)/2+1$
3050	05244	$-1-23+4*(56-7+89A-B)$	$B+A-9+(-8-7*6*5)*-4*-3*-2*1$
3051	05245	$-12+3*45*-6*-7+8-9AB$	$-B+A*-9*8*-7+(-65+4)*-3-2-1$
3052	05246	$1-2-3*(4+5+6+7-(8+9*-A))*-B$	$BA+98*(76-5-4-32+1)$
3053	05247	$-1-(-234+5*-678)-(-9-AB)$	$B*(-A9-(87-6-(54+3)))*(-2-1)$
3054	05248	$1-2*34*-56-7+89-AB$	$-BA9-(-8+7*-654)+321$
3055	05249	$1+2345-6+7+8+9A*B$	$B+A-9*(8-7*-6-(5*4+3*2))-1$
3056	05250	$-123-(4-5*(678-(-9A-B)))$	$B-A+987+65*(43-2+1)$
3057	05251	$12-3-4*(-56-789-AB)$	$-BA-98*-7*-6+54+321$
3058	05252	$1-(2-345+6)-7*(8*9-A)*-B$	$B+A-9+8*7+6*5*4/3/2*1$
3059	05253	$12+3+4*(5+6-7+89A+A)*B$	$B+A-9+8*7+6*5*4/3/2+1$
305A	05254	$1+23-45*-67+89*A-B$	$BA+98*7*-6-5*(-43+2+1)$
305B	05255	$-1*(-2-3)*(4-56+789*(-A+B))$	$BA+987-6*(-5-432)*1$
3060	05256	$-123-4*(-5-67-89A)+B$	$B-A*-98+(-76-5)*(-4-32-1)$
3061	05257	$-1+23+4*(-5+678)+9AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7*(-6*5-4*3-2)^1$
3062	05258	$-1*(-2+3*4*(56+78-9A))*-B$	$BA-9*-8*(-7+65)+43+21$
3063	05259	$-1-234*(-5-6)+7*(89+AB)$	$B+A+9*(8-7*6+5*4-3*2)^1$
3064	05260	$-1*(-2-3)*(4+56+789-AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8-7*6+5*4)*3*2+1$
3065	05261	$-1+2*-3*(456-(78+9AB))$	$B+A+9+(-8-7*6*5)*-4*3*2-1$
3066	05262	$-1*(23-4-5*(678-(9-A*B)))$	$-BA-(-9+8+76*5*4*3-(-2+1))$
3067	05263	$-1+2345-6*-7+89A+B$	$B-A+9-87*(-65+43-21)$
3068	05264	$-1*(23+4-5+6*7*8)*(-9-A+B)$	$BA98-76*5*(-4+32)*-1$
3069	05265	$-1*-23*(-4+56+7+89A+A+B)$	$-B-A-(9+8+76*-54+321)$
306A	05266	$-1+2345+6*(78+9A+B)$	$BA-9-876+5*43*21$
306B	05267	$-1+2*34*56+(-7-8)*(-9A+B)$	$B+A*9*-8*-7+6+5*(-4-32)*-1$
3070	05268	$1+2345-(-6*7*8-9*-A*-B)$	$BA9+876+543*(2+1)$
3071	05269	$123+4-567*-8-9A*B$	$-B+A*(-9+8)*(76-5-432+1)$
3072	05270	$1*(-23-4)*(-56-78+9-A-B)$	$B+A98+7+65*(43-2-1)$
3073	05271	$1+2345-(6+78)+9AB$	$BA9-(876+54*3*21)$
3074	05272	$12+34+(-5+67)*8*9+A*-B$	$-BA-98-7*(6-543-21)$
3075	05273	$1-2*(-3-4*(5+6))*7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A9-876-5*-43*21$
3076	05274	$1*-2*-3*(-4+56+7+89-A-B)$	$-B-A-9*8*(-7-6)*5+432+1$
3077	05275	$-1+2*-3*4*-5*-6*-7+89+AB$	$B+A+9*8+(-7+6*5+4)/-3*-2*1$
3078	05276	$-1*(234-567*8-(-9A))-B$	$-BA-9*8-76*(54-3)*(-2+1)$
3079	05277	$1-2+34*5+6*7*8*9+A*B$	$-BA+98+76*54-321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
307A	05278	-1+2345+67+89A-B	B+A+9*8+(7+6-5+4 ³) ² +1
307B	05279	1*2345+67+89A-B	-BA9-8+7*(6-(5+43))*-21
3080	05280	-1+2345-67-8+9AB	-B-A-(-987+65*-43)-21
3081	05281	-1+2345+6-78+9AB	-B+A-98-76*-5*4*3+2*-1
3082	05282	1*2345+6-78+9AB	-BA-9-(8-7*(6+543))-2*-1
3083	05283	1+2345+6-78+9AB	B+A-(-9-87*(-6+5)*43*(-2+1))
3084	05284	1+(-2+3 ⁴)*(5+6+7*8)-9+A-B	BA+9-(876-5*-43*-21)
3085	05285	-1-23-(45*(-6-78)-9)-A*-B	B-(A98-7*-65)+4321
3086	05286	123+456*(7-8+9)-(A+B)	B+A98+7-654*(-3-2+1)
3087	05287	-1-2-3-4*5*6*-7*8-9AB	BA9-8*-76*5-43+21
3088	05288	-1+23*4-(-567+89A)*-B	BA9-8*76*-5-(-4+3)*-21
3089	05289	-1234+5*6+7*(-89+A)*-B	-B-A*9*8*-7+6-5*-43-2+1
308A	05290	123-4-56*7*-8+9AB	-BA9+87+6*(-5+43)*21
308B	05291	1+2-3-(-456+789A)*-B	-B*(A9-8+76*-5+4*32*-1)
3090	05292	12*-3*(4+5+6+7-8-9-AB)	B+A+9*8*7+6+(5+4 ³) ² +1
3091	05293	-12-34-56*(-78+9)-AB	-BA-9+8-7*(-6-543)-2-1
3092	05294	-1+2-3456+789*A-B	B+A+9+8*(7*6+5 ⁴ -3 ²) ¹
3093	05295	1-2*-3*456+7+8+9AB	B+A+9*(8-7*6+5 ⁴ -3-2) ¹
3094	05296	1234-5*-6*(-7+8+9A-B)	-B-A-9*-87*6+5*(-43+2*1)
3095	05297	1*2345-(67-8-9AB)	-B+A98+7*(-65+432-1)
3096	05298	-123+4+5+6*7*(8-9+AB)	-BA+9-8+7*(-6-543)*(-2+1)
3097	05299	1-((-2-3)*4 ⁵ +6*7-8)-9)+A-B	-B-A+9*8*7*(6+5-4/3 ²) ¹
3098	05300	-1+2345+67-(-89A-B)	-BA+9*87*6+5*-4*-3*-2*1
3099	05301	-12-3456-789*-A+B	-BA-9-8-7*-6*5*(43-21)
309A	05302	1*(23-4+5*-67+8-9A)*-B	B*(A-9-(-8-76)-54*3*2*-1)
309B	05303	-1-2*-3*-4*(-5-67-(8+9A+B))	-B-A-987*6-5*5*432*1
30A0	05304	1*-2*-3*-4*(-56-7-8-9-AB)	-B+A98+7*(65-432)*-1
30A1	05305	-1+2345-6-(-7*-8-9AB)	-B-A9-8-7*(-6-(543+2)*1)
30A2	05306	1-23-(-456-7)*8+9+AB	-B-A+987-65*-43+2-1
30A3	05307	12-3456-789*-A-B	-B-A9+8+7*(6+543)*2(-1)
30A4	05308	-12+345-6*-78*9-AB	BA-9*(-87-654+321)
30A5	05309	-12-(-3456+7*8*9)-(A-B)	B+A+(-9+8-7*6)*(5-4 ³ +2)-1
30A6	05310	1*-2*-3*(456-(-7-89-AB))	BA9-8-7*(6-(54+321))
30A7	05311	1+2345+67-8-9A*-B	B-A-9*-87*-6+5*-43-(-2-1)
30A8	05312	123-45*(-67-(8+9)-(-A+B))	-BA-9*(8-7)*-6*(54-(-32+1))
30A9	05313	-123+456+(-8-9)*AB	-B*(A+9-87-6+54-321)
30AA	05314	-1+2345-6*(7-89-AB)	-BA-(-98-7*(-6-(-543+2)))
30AB	05315	(-1+2-3 ⁴ -5/6+7)*-8*9+A-B	-B-A+98-76*(-54+3-(-2-1))
30B0	05316	-12+3+4*(56-7+89A)+B	B+A-(-9+(8-76)*54-32*1)
30B1	05317	-1-2+34-56*(-78-9+A+B)	-BA-98+7+654*(3+2+1)
30B2	05318	1+234-5*-678+(9+A)*B	B+A+9+8*(7*6+5 ⁴ -3*2) ¹
30B3	05319	1-(-2345-6-(-7*8+9AB))	-B-(-A-9-8+76*-54+321)
30B4	05320	12*(345-(67-(89-AB)))	BA+9*8-8-7*6*5*(4-3)*21
30B5	05321	1-(2-345)-(-6*78*9+AB)	BA-9+8-7*(6-543+21)
30B6	05322	1*2*-3*(-45-678-9+AB)	B-(-A-987-65*43+2+1)
30B7	05323	123+45-6*78*-9+AB	B+A-9+8+76*54-321
30B8	05324	(1+2+3*4)*5*(6+7*8+9)+A-B	B*(A-(9-87)-6*-54-(3+2)+1)
30B9	05325	1-2+34+5-6*-7*(8+9A)-B	-BA9-8*-7*-6-(-5-4321)
30BA	05326	1+2345-6+78-9A*-B	BA9-(-8+7*(6-54-321))
30BB	05327	1+2345-(-67-8)+9A*B	B+A98-(7*(65-432)-1)
3100	05328	-12-3-4+(5-67)*-8*9+A+B	-B+A+987-65*-43+2+1
3101	05329	12-3456-(-789*A-B)	BA-98+76*54-321
3102	05330	-123+4-5-6*-7*(-8+9)*AB	-B-A+987+65*43+21
3103	05331	(-1-2 ³ (3+4)+5)*(-6*7+8-9)+A-B	-BA9-87-654*3*2*-1
3104	05332	-12+3*(4+5)*-6*(-7-(-89+AB))	-BA9+8-7*(6-543)+2+1
3105	05333	-1+23-45*-67-8*(-9-AB)	B+A98+7*(-65+432+1)
3106	05334	12+34*(-56+78+9A-B)	B+A-9-8+(7+6+5*4*3) ² +1
3107	05335	-1+2-345-67*8*-9+AB	B*(-A-98-(-76-54-321))
3108	05336	1*(23-4)*(5-6)*(-78-9-AB)	-BA+9*87*6-5-4-3*21
3109	05337	123+45*(-6+78+9)+AB	B-A+98*(7-6-5+43-2+1)
310A	05338	1234-5*6*7*-8-9+AB	-BA+987-65*(-43-2)*1
310B	05339	1-234+5*(-6+789)+AB	-BA+987-65*(-43-2)+1
3110	05340	-1+2+3+4*(5-6-78+9AB)	-BA+9-8*(76-543)+21
3111	05341	-1-(-2 ³ +3 ⁴)*-6*-7/-8+9+A-B	B+A+9*8*7*(6+5-4/3 ²) ¹
3112	05342	1-(2-345+6*78*-9-A*-B)	B+A98-(76+54-3)*-21
3113	05343	-12-3-4*(-56+7-89A-B)	B+A98+7*-65*(-4-3)-(-2-1)
3114	05344	1+23+45*(6+78)-9+AB	B+A*-98+7*-65*-4*3+21
3115	05345	1-(234-5+67*8*-9+A)-B	B-A9*-8-(765*-4-32*-1)
3116	05346	-1*(2-3)*(-4-5*(-6-78))*(-9+A)*B	B+A-(-987-65*43+2-1)
3117	05347	-1-2+34+5*(-6+7+89*A+B)	B-A9-(87-654*-3*-2*1)
3118	05348	12*(345-6+7-89-A+B)	BA9+8*76*5-4+32+1
3119	05349	(-1-(2+3) ⁴ +(-5-6)*7+8)/9-(A-B)	-BA9+87*(65-4)-321
311A	05350	1*(-2-3-(-45+6)-78)*(-9A+B)	B+A-(-987-65*43-2)+1
311B	05351	12-3+4*(-5-67-8+9AB)	B+A-9*-8*76-(5-43)*-21
3120	05352	-1*-2*(3-4567+8*-9A*-B)	-B-(A98+76*5-4321)
3121	05353	1+23*-4*5-6*(-789+AB)	BA9-8*-7*(-6-5-(-43-21))
3122	05354	1-2-3+45*67-8+9*AB	B-A+9*-8-7*(6+543-2)*-1
3123	05355	-1*(2-3)*(4*-56-78+9AB)	-B+A*987+65*4*(-3-21)
3124	05356	-1-23+4*(-56-7-8+9AB)	B-A-(9+87-65)*43*(-2-1)
3125	05357	12-3*4*5*6*-7+8+(9+A)*-B	-B*(A-9)*(-87+65-(4+321))
3126	05358	-1+2345+6-7-8+9AB	B+A+9+(8+7*6+5*4+3) ² -1
3127	05359	1*2345+6-7-8+9AB	B-(-A-98*7*6-5)-(-4-321)
3128	05360	-1+2345-6+7-8+9AB	-BA9+8*(-7-6*5)+4321
3129	05361	-1*(-2345+6-7-(-8+9AB))	B-A*98+765*(4+3-(2-1))
312A	05362	-1-(-2345+6-(-7+8+9AB))	BA-9*-87*6-(5+4)*32*1
312B	05363	-1*(-23-4)*(-5+67-(8-(9A-B)))	B+A+9+8+(7+6+5+4) ³ /2+1
3130	05364	1-(-2345+6)-7-(-8-9AB)	-BA+987-6-(5+4)*-321
3131	05365	1+2*-34*-56+78-9-A+B	B-(A9+8)-76*(-54+3)-(-2+1)
3132	05366	1-2*-34-5*(-678+9-A*B)	B+A+9+8+(7+6+5*4*3) ² -1
3133	05367	1-234-(-5+67*-8*9+A-B)	B-A9-8*76*(54-3)-(-2-1)
3134	05368	1*(23-(456-789+A))*B	B+A+9+8+(7+6+5*4*3) ² +1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3135	05369	$-12-(3+4-5^*(678-9+AB))$	$-B+A9+8-7-(-6-54)^*-3^*-21$
3136	05370	$-1-2-3^*4+5^*(67+8+9^*A^*B)$	$B-(A-9+8)-7^*(6-543-2)-1$
3137	05371	$1-(23+45^*-67)-(-8+9A)^*-B$	$BA9-8^*7+6^*(5+432^*1)$
3138	05372	$1+2^*-3^*-456-(-78-9AB)$	$B-A-98+76^*(54-3)-2-1$
3139	05373	$-1+2345+6+(7-8)^*-9AB$	$-BA+98+76^*5^*4^*3-2+1$
313A	05374	$1+2345+6+7-8+9AB$	$BA-98+7^*(6+543-2+1)$
313B	05375	$-1-23+45+(-6+7^*8)^*(9A-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7^*6-5^*4)+3^*2^*1$
3140	05376	$1^*(2+34)^*(-5+6)^*(7-8+9A+B)$	$B-A-9+8-7^*(6-543-2-1)$
3141	05377	$1-2^*3+4^*5^*6^*7/8+9A-B$	$-B-A9+87^*(-6+54)-321$
3142	05378	$1+2345-6-(-7-8-9AB)$	$-B+A+9-(-8+7^*(6-543-(2-1)))$
3143	05379	$-1-23-45+6^*7^*(8-9+AB)$	$-B^*(A9-87+6-54-321)$
3144	05380	$1+234-5-67^*-8^*(9A-B)$	$-BA-9^*87^*-6-(5-4+32)-1$
3145	05381	$-1-2^*-3^*(4-56-(78^*-9-AB))$	$-B+A-9^*-8-76^*(-5-43-2-1)$
3146	05382	$-12+3^*(456+789)+AB$	$-BA9+8^*76+5^*43^*21$
3147	05383	$-12-3^*45^*-6^*7-89A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8-7)+6+5^*4)^*(3^*2+1)$
3148	05384	$-1^*(2-3)^*4^*(5+6-(78-9AB))$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6+5-4-32+1$
3149	05385	$12+3+4^*(5-(-6-(78+9)))+A)^*B$	$B+A+9^*(8-7^*6+5^*4+3+2)^*1$
314A	05386	$-1-2+3^*-456-7^*(-89+A)^*B$	$-BA-98+7^*654+321$
314B	05387	$1-2^*-3+4^*(5-67-(8-9AB))$	$BA9+876-54^*-32^*1$
3150	05388	$-1+2345+6+7+8+9AB$	$BA9+876-54^*-32+1$
3151	05389	$1^*2+3+4^*5^*6^*7/8+9A-B$	$-BA+9^*-87^*-6-(-43+21))$
3152	05390	$1-(-2345-(6+7))(-8-9AB)$	$-B^*(-A9+8+7+65+4-321)$
3153	05391	$1+2^*3+4^*5^*6^*7/8+9A-B$	$BA+987+65^*(43-2+1)$
3154	05392	$1^*2^*3+4^*5^*6^*7/8+9A-B$	$-BA+98-7^*(6^*-54-3)^*2^*1$
3155	05393	$-12+3-4^*(5-(-67+8+9AB))$	$-B-A^*(-9-8-76)^*5+43+2+1$
3156	05394	$1^*-2^*(-3+45-67)^*(8^*9+A+B)$	$B+A+9^*-87^*-6+5^*4^*-3+2+1$
3157	05395	$-12+3+4-567^*-8-9^*-A^*-B$	$BA-98-7^*(-6+543+2)^*-1$
3158	05396	$(-1-2^*3^*-4^*5)^*(6^*7-8)-9A-B$	$BA^*(98+7-65-4-3-2+1)$
3159	05397	$123+45^*67-89^*-A-B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6+5)^*4^*(3+2-1)$
315A	05398	$1^*2^*(-3^*(45-678)-9A-B)$	$-B-A+98+76^*54-321$
315B	05399	$1-234+5^*(6+789)+AB$	$-BA9+8^*-7^*(-65-43-(-2+1))$
3160	05400	$-1^*-23^*(45+6-7-(-8-9-AB))$	$-BA-9^*8-7^*(-6-543-21)$
3161	05401	$-1+2345-6^*-7-8+9AB$	$BA9-87^*-6+5^*-432^*-1$
3162	05402	$-12-34^*5^*-67+8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A9-8^*-76+5^*4^*3^*21$
3163	05403	$-1234-5-6^*(-789-AB)$	$-B-A-9+8-76^*-5^*-4^*-3+21$
3164	05404	$12+3^*-4+567^*8-9^*A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(8+7+6-(5^*4-3^*2))^+1$
3165	05405	$-1+2345+67+(8+9A)^*B$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6^*(5-4+3)^*2-1$
3166	05406	$-12-34+5^*6^*-7^*(89-AB)$	$BA9-8-7+6^*(5+432-1)$
3167	05407	$-123+4+5^*(-6+789+A)-B$	$BA9+8^*-7^*-6-54+321$
3168	05408	$1-2+3+4-567^*-8+9^*-A^*B$	$B-(A98-7^*654-321)$
3169	05409	$1234+5^*678-9AB$	$BA9+8^*7^*-6^*(54+3^*-21)$
316A	05410	$-12+3-4-5^*(-678-(9A+B))$	$B-(A+9)-(-87^*6+54^*-3^*21)$
316B	05411	$123+4^*(56+789+AB)$	$-BA-9+87^*-6^*(5+4)^*(-3+2)^*1$
3170	05412	$12-3456-78^*(9-AB)$	$BA9-8^*-7^*65-432+1$
3171	05413	$-1234+5-6^*(-789-AB)$	$-B+A9-8-76^*-54-321$
3172	05414	$-1+2-3^*4^*56^*-7^*(-8+9)-AB$	$-B-A9-(8+7)-(-654^*-3^*-2-1)$
3173	05415	$-12-(-3+4+5^*(6-789+A+B))$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7^*6-5^*4-3^*2)+1$
3174	05416	$-1-2-3+4^*5^*6^*-7^*-8+9A^*B$	$-BA-9-(8-7)-654^*-3^*-2^*-1$
3175	05417	$-1+2+34^*-5^*-67-8^*-9A^*-B$	$BA9-87^*6^*-5+432^*1$
3176	05418	$-1^*(-2345+6+7^*-8-9AB)$	$-B+A+98+76^*54-321$
3177	05419	$1+2345-6+7^*8+9AB$	$B-A-9^*(8-(7-6-5+432^*1))$
3178	05420	$1+2-34-56^*(-78+9)-(A+B)$	$B-A+98-76^*-54-321$
3179	05421	$12-(345-6^*(789-AB))$	$-B-(A-(9+8^*(-76-(-543+2))))+1$
317A	05422	$-1-23^*-4-5^*(-678-9A+B)$	$-B-A9-(-8+7+654)^*3^*2^*-1$
317B	05423	$1+234-5+6^*7^*8^*9+AB$	$-B^*(A9-(876-(5+432+1)))$
3180	05424	$1^*-2^*(3-(4^*-5^*6+(-7-8)^*-9^*(A+B)))$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*6-5^*-4^*(3+2)+1$
3181	05425	$-1^*(2+3-4)^*-5^*(678+9A+B)$	$-B-(A-98)+7^*(-6+543)-21$
3182	05426	$-1+2-34+5^*(6-(78+9^*-AB))$	$-B-A-(-9+8)-7^*(-6-(543+2-1))$
3183	05427	$1-2^*(-3+45)^*67-89-A+B$	$-B-A9-8+7-654^*3^*2^*-1$
3184	05428	$12+3^*4+567^*8-9^*-A^*-B$	$-B+A9^*(-8+7)+654^*-3^*-2^*1$
3185	05429	$-1+2^*3^*(4-5+678)-(9-(A+B))$	$-BA+9^*(8+76+54+321)$
3186	05430	$-1^*(2-3)^*-4-(56-78)^*(9-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9^*8-7-(6-5^*4)^*3^*2/1$
3187	05431	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4^*5-6^*7^*8-9)$	$-B-A-(-9^*8-7^*(-6+543))^+21$
3188	05432	$-1+2^*3+456^*7+8^*9A-B$	$-BA-9+8+7+654^*(3-(-2-1))$
3189	05433	$-1234+56^*78+9AB$	$-B-A9-8^*76+5^*-43^*21$
318A	05434	$-1234-5^*(-67-(-8+9AB))$	$-B^*(A+9+87-(6-5+432+1))$
318B	05435	$-12-(-3+45^*-67-(89A-B))$	$B+A9-8-76^*-54-321$
3190	05436	$1+2+3-4+(-56+78)^*(9-A)^*-B$	$B-A+9^*-8^*(-7-65)-432+1$
3191	05437	$1-2-34-56^*(-78+9)^*(-A+B)$	$B-A9^*-8^*7+6^*5-4^*321$
3192	05438	$-1-(-2345-67+8-9AB)$	$B-A-9-8^*(76-543)-2^*1$
3193	05439	$1^*2345-(-67-(-8+9AB))$	$B-A-(-98^*7+6^*-543^*(2-1))$
3194	05440	$1+2345-(-67+8)+9AB$	$-B-(-A98+7-65^*43+21)$
3195	05441	$-12-345+6^*(7-8)^*9^*A^*-B$	$-BA-9^*87^*-6-5+4-3+21$
3196	05442	$1-(2-3)-4^*(56-7+8-9AB)$	$BA9+8+7+6^*(-5-432)^*-1$
3197	05443	$1-234-5^*-678-9^*A^*-B$	$-B-(A9-8-7+654^*3^*2^*-1)$
3198	05444	$12+34-5^*(-678+9-AB)$	$BA-(9-8)-(-76^*-54+321)$
3199	05445	$-1-2^*(3+4)+5^*6^*7^*(8-9+AB)$	$B^*(-A9+8-7+65-4)^*3^*(-2-1)$
319A	05446	$12^*(-3-(45+6^*-78)-(9A-B))$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6+54-32^*1$
319B	05447	$-12-3+4+5^*6^*7^*(8-9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(7-6-5^*4^*3)+2+1$
31A0	05448	$-1^*-2^*-3^*(4+567+89)^*(A-B)$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6-5-4+32-1$
31A1	05449	$1+23-4-5^*(-678-9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*-7^*(6+5)-4)/3^*-2+1$
31A2	05450	$1-(2-3)+4^*(-56-7-(-8-9AB))$	$B+A98+765^*4-321$
31A3	05451	$-12-3+45^*67+89A+B$	$-B+A9-(8+7^*(-6-(-543+2)))^*-1$
31A4	05452	$1-(-2-3)-45^*-67-(-89A+B)$	$B-A9-(-8+7)+654^*3^*2+1$
31A5	05453	$-1+23+4^*(5+67+89A)+B$	$B-A-9+8+7^*(-6-543-2)^*-1$
31A6	05454	$-1-(-2-3456-7^*-8^*9-AB)$	$-BA+9-8^*7^*-65-43^*-21$
31A7	05455	$1+2345-(-6-78-9AB)$	$-B-A^*9^*-8^*7+6^*(-5+43+21)$
31A8	05456	$-1^*(23-456-7+8+9A)^*B$	$B^*(A-9)^*(876-543+21)$
31A9	05457	$-12+3-45^*-67+89A+B$	$B-(A-(-9-87))-654^*3^*2^*-1$
31AA	05458	$-12-3+4^*(5+6)^*78+9AB$	$-BA-9^*87^*-6-5+4+32+1$
31AB	05459	$-12-3-(456^*-7+8+9^*A^*-B)$	$-BA+9-8^*(-7-65-432-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
31B0	05460	$-12*(-34+56)*(78-9A+B)$	$-BA-9^*-8+7*(-6+543+21)$
31B1	05461	$-123+4-5+(6^7-8+9)^*AB$	$-B-A+9+8*(-76+543)+21$
31B2	05462	$-1-2-3-45^*-67+89A+B$	$-BA+9-876^*-5-(432+1)$
31B3	05463	$1-2*(-3^4+5-6^*-7^8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*(-76+543-2)+1$
31B4	05464	$-12-3+4+56*(78-9)+A-B$	$-BA+98+76*(54-3)*(2-1)$
31B5	05465	$-1+2345-(-6-78-9AB)$	$-B-A-9+8-(76*(54+3)+2)-1$
31B6	05466	$1^*2345-(-6-78-9AB)$	$BA+987-65^*-43-2^*1$
31B7	05467	$1+2345-(-6-78)+9AB$	$B*(A9-87-(-654+321))$
31B8	05468	$1+2-3+45^*67-(-89A-B)$	$BA+987-65^*-43*(2-1)$
31B9	05469	$-1234+5^*-67+8^*9^*-A^*-B$	$BA9-8^*-76^*5-4*(-32-1)$
31BA	05470	$-1+23+4^*(5-(67-8-9AB))$	$BA+987-65^*-43+2^*1$
31BB	05471	$12-34-(5+6^*7*(-8+9))^*-AB$	$BA9+87-6^*(5-432)+1$
3200	05472	$123^*4*(-5-6-(7+89)+AB)$	$BA-98^*7^*-6-(-5+4-321)$
3201	05473	$1-(2-345)-(-6^*78^*-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9+(8+7*(6+5))^*4^3+2+1$
3202	05474	$-1+2-3-4+5^*(678-(-9-AB))$	$-BA+9*(876-(5+432)+1)$
3203	05475	$123-4-(-5+6^*-7*(8+9A))+B$	$B+A+9-(876+5)^*4+321$
3204	05476	$1-234+5-67^*-8^*9+A^*B$	$-BA9-(87+65-4321)$
3205	05477	$1+2+345-6^*78^*-9+A+B$	$-BA98+765^*-4^*3^*-2+1$
3206	05478	$1*(-234+567+8+9+A)^*B$	$B-A9-876^*-5-432^*1$
3207	05479	$1+2^*-3+4567-(-8+9)^*AB$	$BA-(9+8-(-7*(6-543))-2+1))$
3208	05480	$1-23+4567-89^*(A+B)$	$B+A-98+7+654^*3^*2^*1$
3209	05481	$-1-2+3-4+5^*(6+789)-A^*B$	$BA9+8^*(-765+432)^*-1$
320A	05482	$1+2-3-45^*(-6-7)^*8-9-A-B$	$BA9-8^*76^*-5+4321$
320B	05483	$(-1+2+3^4+5/-6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A^*-98+765^*4-3^*-2^*-1$
3210	05484	$1+2345-6^*-78+9^*-A^*-B$	$-B-A9-8^*-7-654^*3^*2^*1$
3211	05485	$12+3+45^*67+89A+B$	$-B+A9-8+76^*-5^*4^*-3-21$
3212	05486	$((-1-2^A(3+4))^*-5+6^*7)^*8-9+A-B$	$BA-9+87+6^*5^*(4+3)^*21$
3213	05487	$1*(-23-4)^*(567+8^*(9-AB))$	$-BA9+8^*-76^*5^*(-4+3)^*-2^*1$
3214	05488	$-12*(-345-6-7+89-A+B)$	$BA9-8^*-76^*5-(-4-3)^*21$
3215	05489	$-1-2345+6-7+8^*9^*AB$	$-B*(A-987+654-32)^*1$
3216	05490	$-12+34+5^*(6+789)-AB$	$BA-9^*8^*7+65^*(43+21)$
3217	05491	$1^*2-(-3^*(-4-5^*-6^*7)+8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8^*(6+54)-(-3+2+1)$
3218	05492	$1+2-(-3^*(-4-5^*-6^*7)+8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA-98^*(6-5)^*-4+32^*1$
3219	05493	$-12+3-45+67^*8^*9-AB$	$BA+987+65^*43+21$
321A	05494	$-1+23-45^*-67+89A+B$	$B+A+9-87+654^*3^*2-1$
321B	05495	$(-1-2/-3^*(-4^*5^*6+7))^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A9^*8+7^*(654+3^*2)^*1$
3220	05496	$1+23+45^*67+89A+B$	$-BA9+8^*(6+54)-3-2^*-1$
3221	05497	$1+(-2^A(3+4)+5^*6)^*-7^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9^*8-7^*(-6-(543-(-2+1)))$
3222	05498	$1-(2+34)-5-6^*7^*(8-9-AB)$	$-BA+98^*76-54^*-3^*-21$
3223	05499	$1-2+34+5^*(-67-8-9^*-AB)$	$-BA-98-(-76^*54-3^*(-2+1))$
3224	05500	$-123+456+7^*-8^*9^*-A-B$	$B*(-A+987-654+32+1)$
3225	05501	$-1+2-(3+4)-(-5+6^*-7*(-8+9))^*AB$	$BA9+8+7-65^*(-43-2^*-1)$
3226	05502	$1^*(2+34)^*(-5-67+89-A^*B)$	$B-A-987-6^*(-5+43)^*-21$
3227	05503	$-1-(2345-6-7-8^*-9^*-AB)$	$-B+A^*9+8^*(-76+543-2-1)$
3228	05504	$-1+2-3+4567+89^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A9^*8+7+6^*(543-21)$
3229	05505	$123+45^*(6+78)+9+A+B$	$-BA-9^*-8+7+654^*3^*2^*1$
322A	05506	$-12+3^*4^*(-567+89A-B)$	$B-A9-8^*-7-654^*3^*2^*1$
322B	05507	$-12-345-6^*(-78-9+A)^*B$	$-B+A-98+(-7+6^*-5)^*4^*-32^*1$
3230	05508	$-1^*2^*-3^*(4+567+8-(-9A+B))$	$-B-(-A9-(-8-76^*5^*-4^*-3+2^*-1))$
3231	05509	$(-1+2^*3)^*4^5-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6+5-4)^3+2-1$
3232	05510	$-1^*(2-(-34-(5-67^*8^*9)))+AB$	$-B+A9-8+76^*(54-3-(2-1))$
3233	05511	$-1-2^*-3^*4^*5+6+78+9+A+B$	$-BA*(-A-9-8+76^*-5-4^*3^*-2^*-1)$
3234	05512	$1^*-2^*(-34+56)^*(-7-(-8+9A)+B)$	$BA9-(87+65^*-43+21)$
3235	05513	$1-2+34-5^*(6-789+A)-B$	$B+A+9+8-((7+(6+5^*4)^3)^*2-1)$
3236	05514	$-1234-5^*(-67-(8+9AB))$	$-BA-9^*8^*-7^*(6+5)-4^*(-3-21)$
3237	05515	$-1^*(2-3-4)^*(5+6+789-(A+B))$	$-B-(A9-8^*-76-5^*43^*21)$
3238	05516	$-12+345-6+7^*8^*9+A+B$	$B+A+9-8+7-(-6-5^*4)^3+2-1$
3239	05517	$1+23+4+5^*(6+789)-A^*B$	$B+A+9-8+7-(6-5^*4)^3+2/1$
323A	05518	$12-(-34+5^*(-6-789))-AB$	$B+A+9-(8-7-6-5-4)^3+2/1$
323B	05519	$-1-(-2-3)-456-(7^*-8+9)^*AB$	$BA-987+65^*-4^*(3-21)$
3240	05520	$1^*(-2-(3-45))^*-6-(-7-(-8-9)-AB))$	$-BA-9+87+654^*3^*2^*1$
3241	05521	$1-(-23-45^*67)-(-8+9A)^*B$	$B-A9^*-87+65^*(43^*-2+1)$
3242	05522	$-1^*(23-(-4+567)+89A)^*B$	$-BA9-(-8^*-76+5^*43^*-21)$
3243	05523	$12-34+5+6^*7^*(-8+9+AB)$	$-BA9-87-6^*5+4321$
3244	05524	$1+2^*3^*4^*56-(-7-89-AB)$	$-BA-(98+76^*-54)-3+21$
3245	05525	$(1+2^*3)^4+5^A(6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$B-(A-9^*8^*76)+5-4-(32+1)$
3246	05526	$12-(34+5)-67^*8^*-9-AB$	$B+A98-(-7+65^*-43-21)$
3247	05527	$12-345+6-7^*-8^*(9A-B)$	$B+A+987-6-(5+4)^*-321$
3248	05528	$-1-2-3^*4+(-5-6)^*-7^*-8^*-9+A-B$	$-B+A^*(9-87)^*-6-(54+32-1)$
3249	05529	$1-23-456^*-7-89^*-A+B$	$B+A+9^*(-8+7-6+5^A-3^*2)^A1$
324A	05530	$-1^*2^*(34-5)^*-67^*(8-9)^*(A-B)$	$B-A-(-9+8^*-76-54^*3^*21)$
324B	05531	$1-23-4^*(56+78)^*-9-AB$	$-B-A9+87+654^*3^*-2^*-1$
3250	05532	$1^*-2^*-3^*(-4+567+8+9-A^*-B)$	$-B-A9+87+654^*-3^*-2+1$
3251	05533	$1+2^*3+456^*7+8^*(9A+B)$	$-B*(A9-8-(765-(4+321)))$
3252	05534	$1+23+4567+89^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-9+8-7)^*-65-432-1$
3253	05535	$1^*23^*(4-5)^*(-6-78-(9A-B))$	$BA-9^*8-76^*(-54+3)-21$
3254	05536	$1-2^*(-3^*-4^5+6^*7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-987-(-6-5))^*-4-32+1$
3255	05537	$-1-(2-3456+(-78+9A))^*B$	$-B-A9-8-76^*-54-3^*21$
3256	05538	$1234-5^*-678-9A^*B$	$-BA^*(9-(-8-7)-(-6-5^*-4+32-1))$
3257	05539	$1-23+45^*(6-7+89-(A-B))$	$B+A^*98+765^*4+3+21$
3258	05540	$1-2-(3-4)-5^*(6-789+A-B)$	$-B+A9+8-7^*(-6-543)-21$
3259	05541	$-12-34+5^*(6+789)^*(A+B)$	$-BA-98-76^*-54+32+1$
325A	05542	$1-(-234+567^*-8)+9^*-AB$	$-B+A98-7-65^*(-43-2+1)$
325B	05543	$123+4-56^*(-78+9)+A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8+(7+6+5-4)^3)^*2^A1$
3260	05544	$1+2-3^*-4^*-56^*-7+8+(9-A)^*B$	$-B*(A9-876-5+432^*1)$
3261	05545	$123+45^*67+8-9^*-AB$	$BA-9^*-87-6^*(-543+21)$
3262	05546	$-12+3456+7^*(-8-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9^*8^*76-5-4-3-21$
3263	05547	$12-34-(5-67^*8^*9)+A^*B$	$B+A+9^*(8-7-6+5^A-3^*2)^A1$
3264	05548	$1-2^*3^*-4^*-5+67^*8^*9-A-B$	$B-(A-9-8-7^*(-6+543+21))$
3265	05549	$-1^*(-23-4)^*(5-67-89)^*(A-B)$	$B+A-9^*-87-6^*-543-21$
3266	05550	$1-(2-3+4+5+67^*-8^*9+AB)$	$-BA-9^*-87^*6+5^*(4-3+21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3267	05551	$-1+2^*-345-6*(78+9*-AB)$	$-B+A-9+87^*-6*(-5-4)-3+2^*1$
3268	05552	$12+3-4-5-6^*7*(8-9-AB)$	$-BA9-87-(6-5-4321)$
3269	05553	$-1-2*(3-4)-5-(67*8^*-9+AB)$	$-BA9-8-76-5+4321$
326A	05554	$1^*-2*(-34^*56-7-8+9-AB)$	$-BA9-87+6-5+4321$
326B	05555	$-12+3+4+5+67^*-8^*-9-AB$	$B*(-A9+876+5-(432-1))$
3270	05556	$123+4-5*(-678-9A)+B$	$-B+A+9^*87^*6-5+4-3-(2-1)$
3271	05557	$-1-2+3+4*(56+78)^*9-AB$	$-B+A*(-9+8^*76)-543^*-2^*-1$
3272	05558	$12+3+4^*-5^*6^*-7^*8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A+9^*(8+7-6-5)-4^*(3^*2-1)$
3273	05559	$-123+4+5*(6+789)+AB$	$B-A-9+76^*54+3^*-21$
3274	05560	$-1-(2-345)-(6^*-78^*9-A^*B)$	$B-A-9-(-8+7)^*-654*(-3-2-1)$
3275	05561	$-1+23*(-4+5+6+78+9A-B)$	$BA+98-76^*-54-321$
3276	05562	$1-2+3^*-4^*-56^*7+8+(9-A)^*-B$	$BA9-87-65^*-43+21$
3277	05563	$-1-(23-4^*-5)-6*(7+8^*-9A)-B$	$-BA9-8-(76-5)+4321$
3278	05564	$1+2345-67^*-8+9^*A^*B$	$-BA9-87+6+5+4321$
3279	05565	$-1-2+3+45*(67-89+AB)$	$-B-A-9-876^*-5-(432+1)$
327A	05566	$1*(-23+4)*(-56-7+89-A)^*-B$	$-B*(-A98+765+4-32-1)$
327B	05567	$-1+23-4^*5^*6^*-7^*8+9^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*8-7+(6+5+4^*3)^*2^*1$
3280	05568	$1-2-(-3-4)+5-67^*8^*-9-AB$	$-BA9+8^*-7*(-65-43-2)+1$
3281	05569	$-12+3456-7-89-AB$	$BA-(-9-87^*6+54^*3^*21)$
3282	05570	$-1*(2345-67+8^*9^*-AB)$	$-BA9-8^*7+6^*-5+4321$
3283	05571	$1-2345+67-8^*9^*-AB$	$-BA9-8-7^*(6+5)+4321$
3284	05572	$-1+23^*-4^*5^*6-7*(-89A+B)$	$BA9-8^*-7^*65-(-4+321)$
3285	05573	$1-2-3+4-5+67^*-8^*-9-A^*B$	$-B+A9*(-8-7-(6-54))+32-1$
3286	05574	$-1^*2^*-3*(-45-(-6+7)^*(8-9^*-A^*-B))$	$-B-A9^*-8-7+6^*-5^*4^*32^*-1$
3287	05575	$1^*2^*3^*4+(5+6)^*7^*8^*9+A-B$	$B-A-9+8+7+654^*-3^*2^*-1$
3288	05576	$-1+2^*-345-6^*-789-AB$	$B-(-A+9^*-87)-(-6^*543-2^*1)$
3289	05577	$(-1+(2^(3+4)+5)^*6)^*7+8-9+A-B$	$B-(-A+9^*-87)-6^*-543-(-2-1)$
328A	05578	$-1-23+45^*67-8+9AB$	$-BA9-8-(-7-(-65+4321))$
328B	05579	$123+4-5*(6-789)-AB$	$-BA9+8-76+5+4321$
3290	05580	$-1-2-(-3456+7)-(89+AB)$	$-BA9+8-7-65+4321$
3291	05581	$-1-2^*345+6*(789-A-B)$	$BA-9+8*(-76+543)^*(2-1)$
3292	05582	$-1-23+45-67^*8^*-9-AB$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6+5-4)^*3^*2+1$
3293	05583	$-12-3456+7-8^*-9AB$	$-B+A9-87+654^*3^*2^*1$
3294	05584	$-1+2+3456-7-89-AB$	$-B-A+9+876^*5+432^*-1$
3295	05585	$12-34^*(-5-6-7)^*8+9^*(-A-B)$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7^*-6^*5+4)^*3+2^*1$
3296	05586	$1+2-(-3456+7+89)-AB$	$BA-98-7+654^*-3^*-2-1$
3297	05587	$1-23+4+56*(78-9)+AB$	$-B-(-A+98^*-7)+6*(543+21)$
3298	05588	$1*(-23+456-789-A)^*-B$	$B*(A98-765+4^*3+21)$
3299	05589	$1^*-23*(-4+5+6-78-(-9+AB))$	$B-A-9+876^*5-432+1$
329A	05590	$12+3456+7*(-8-9)-AB$	$B+A-9^*-87^*6+5-4-3^*-2^*1$
329B	05591	$-1+23+45*(67-89+AB)$	$B+A+9^*-8^*-7^*(6+5)+43-21$
32A0	05592	$1^*-2^*3^*-4^*(5*(67-8)+9-AB)$	$-B-A98-7^*6^*5+4321$
32A1	05593	$1-2+3456-78-9-AB$	$B+A+9-8^*7-6+5^*4^*3^*2^*1$
32A2	05594	$-1-(2-3456-7)-(89+AB)$	$-BA9+8+7-65+4321$
32A3	05595	$-123-4-5^*-678-9^*-A^*B$	$-B-(A+98)-(-76^*-54+3)-21$
32A4	05596	$-1+23-4+5*(6+789)-A-B$	$-BA+9+8+76^*54-(32+1)$
32A5	05597	$12+3456-7-89-AB$	$BA-9-8^*(7-65-432+1)$
32A6	05598	$-12+3456-78-(-9+AB)$	$BA-9-87+654^*3^*2^*1$
32A7	05599	$1^*2+3456+7-89-AB$	$BA+9+8^*(76-543)^*(-2+1)$
32A8	05600	$1+2+3456+7-(89+AB)$	$-BA9-8^*7^*(6-5)+4321$
32A9	05601	$-12+3456-78-9-A^*B$	$-BA-98+7+65^*(43+21)$
32AA	05602	$-1-(2-3456+78)-9A-B$	$BA-98+7+654^*3^*2+1$
32AB	05603	$1-2-(-3456+7)-(89+A^*B)$	$-BA9-87^*-65-432-1$
32B0	05604	$1-2+3456-78-9A-B$	$-BA9-87^*-65-432^*1$
32B1	05605	$-1+2+3456-7-89+A^*-B$	$-BA9-87^*-65-432+1$
32B2	05606	$12+3^*-4*(5+678-9AB)$	$BA-9^*-87^*6+5+43^*-2-1$
32B3	05607	$-123+4^*-5-67^*-8^*9+A^*B$	$B-(A-9^*87^*6-(-5+43-2)^*1)$
32B4	05608	$-1*(23+45+67^*8^*-9^*(-A+B))$	$B-A-98-76^*-54-(32-1)$
32B5	05609	$-1-2+3456-78+9-AB$	$-B-A^*(98+76-543+2+1)$
32B6	05610	$-1^*2^*-3*(-45+6+789-AB)$	$-BA-9^*-8^*7^*(6+5)-(-43+21)$
32B7	05611	$12+3456-(-7+89)-AB$	$-BA9-8-(7-6^*-5-4321)$
32B8	05612	$-1+23-(-4-(-5+6))^*789-(-A-B)$	$-BA+9^*-87^*-6+54^*3^*(2-1)$
32B9	05613	$-12+3456-78-(9A-B)$	$B-(A9-8)-(-76^*-54+32-1)$
32BA	05614	$12*(345-67+89+A^*-B)$	$BA9-8+7-65^*-43-21$
32BB	05615	$1+2+3456-78+9-AB$	$-B+A*(98-76^*-5-4)-3^*2^*-1$
3300	05616	$-1^*-2^*-3^*4*(-56+78)^*-9^*(-A+B)$	$BA9-(-8-(-7+65^*43-21))$
3301	05617	$1^*2+3456-78-9-A^*B$	$-B-A9+876^*5-(-4+321)$
3302	05618	$-1-2-(34-56+789A)^*-B$	$-B-A-9-8^*(76-(543+21))$
3303	05619	$123+4*(-56-7+89AB)$	$B+A+9^*87^*6-5+4+32-1$
3304	05620	$-1-2^*-345^*6-(78+9A-B)$	$B+A+9^*(8-7)^*(6+5^*4-3^*2)+1$
3305	05621	$1-23-4^*5+67^*-8^*-9-(A+B)$	$-B*(-A+9+87+6-5-432)^*1$
3306	05622	$-12-(-3456-7)-8+9^*(-A-B)$	$BA+987-65*(-43-2)^*1$
3307	05623	$-1+23-45-6-7^*-8^*(-9-A^*-B)$	$BA-(9-(8+7))-(-65+4)^*-3^*-21$
3308	05624	$-1-(2-3456)-(78+9A-B)$	$-BA+9-876^*-5+4-321$
3309	05625	$1^*-2+3456-78-9A+B$	$-BA9-8+7-6^*5+4321$
330A	05626	$1-2+3456-(78+9A-B)$	$-BA+9-8-76^*-54-3^*-2+1$
330B	05627	$123-4+5^*6^*7*(-89+AB)$	$B+A-98^*-7-6+54^*3^*21$
3310	05628	$-1+2+3456-78-9A+B$	$BA9-8-7+65^*43+2+1$
3311	05629	$1-2+3456+7+8^*-9-AB$	$-B+A9^*8+7-6^*-543-21$
3312	05630	$-12-(3+456*(-7+8)^*-9)-AB$	$-BA9-(87-(65+4321))$
3313	05631	$-1-2^*3-(-4-5)^*(-67^*-8+9)-AB$	$-B+A98^*7-(-6-54)^*3^*-21$
3314	05632	$12+3456+7-89-A^*B$	$B*(-A9+87-(-65-(4+321)))$
3315	05633	$-12-3-45*(-6-(78+9))-A-B$	$B-A9-8-76^*-54-(3-2)^*1$
3316	05634	$-12-(-3456-7^*-8)-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9-8-76^*-54-3+21$
3317	05635	$-12-3-4^*(5-6+7-(-8+9AB))$	$-BA9-8^*-7-65+4321$
3318	05636	$12+3+45*(-6-7)^*-8-(-9A+B)$	$B+A+9^*(8-7)^*6^*5^*4-3^*2-1$
3319	05637	$-1-23-(4-5-67^*8+9A)^*B$	$-B+A-98-(-76^*54-3^*2^*-1)$
331A	05638	$1-2-3-45+6*(7-8^*-9A)-B$	$B+A98+7^*-6-(5+4)^*-321$
331B	05639	$12+3+45^*67+8+9AB$	$-B+A+98^*76+54^*3^*-21$
3320	05640	$-1-(-23+456^*-7+8^*(-9-AB))$	$-BA9-(8+7)-6+5+4321$
3321	05641	$12+3456-78-9A+B$	$-B-A-9+87-654^*3^*-2^*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3322	05642	$1-23+4+(-56+7)*-8*(-9+A+B)$	$-BA9-(8+7-6+5)+4321$
3323	05643	$-1*(2+34-567+89A)*-B$	$B-(A+98+76*54)-(3-2+1)$
3324	05644	$12+3456-(-7-8*-9)-AB$	$-BA9-(8-7+6+5)+4321$
3325	05645	$1-23+456+7*-8*9*-A-B$	$BA-9*-87*6-54+3-2*-1$
3326	05646	$1+2*3+4^5*6-7*8*9+A-B$	$-B+A-9+8*-7*(-65+4-3-21)$
3327	05647	$-1-23+(4+56+7)*-8*-9+AB$	$-B-A-9-(8-76*54+3*21)$
3328	05648	$1-(-2-3)-(-4-56)*(7+89-A-B)$	$BA-(-987+6+(-5-4)*321)$
3329	05649	$-12+3456-(7*8+9A)+B$	$-B+A-98+76*54+3*-2*-1$
332A	05650	$1-(2-3456)-(-7*-8+9-A*-B)$	$-B-A9+8-76*-54-(3-21)$
332B	05651	$1-2+(-345+678)*(-9+A+B)$	$B-A9+8-76*-54+3-2*1$
3330	05652	$-1*2*(3-(4+5))*(78+9AB)$	$-BA9-(8+7-6-5-4321)$
3331	05653	$(1*2+3)*(4^5+6)+7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA9-8-(7-6)*-5+4321$
3332	05654	$1-2+3456-78+9*-A+B$	$B*(A9+8+7*6-((54-3)*2+1))$
3333	05655	$1+2-(34-5+6*7-8*9)+A-B$	$-BA9-8+7*(6-5)+4321$
3334	05656	$-1-(2-3)-45-(67*8*-9-(A+B))$	$-BA9+9-(8+7*6-54-32+1)$
3335	05657	$-12+3456-7-8-9-AB$	$BA-9*8*7*-6+5-43-2+1$
3336	05658	$12+3456+7*(89-AB)$	$BA9-8*7*(-65-(-4-3))+21$
3337	05659	$-1+2*3456+7*-8*(9A-B)$	$-BA+98+76*54+3*-21$
3338	05660	$12+3-45*(-6+7-89)+AB$	$-BA9+8+7-6-5+4321$
3339	05661	$-1+23-45+67*8*-9*(A-B)$	$-B-A-98+76*54+3*2*1$
333A	05662	$12+3456+7*-8+9-AB$	$B-A-9+87+65*4*-3*-2-1$
333B	05663	$(-1+2+3+4^5)*6-7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8+76*54+3+21$
3340	05664	$-1-23+456*78-9*A+B$	$BA9-8+7+65*43+21$
3341	05665	$-1*-2*((-3*-4*-5*-6-7)*8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A9+8+76*54+3*2-1$
3342	05666	$1-23+456*78-9*A+B$	$B-A*9*8*-7+(-6+5)*(-432-1)$
3343	05667	$12-34+5-67*8*-9*(-A+B)$	$B+A-98*-7*6+543+2+1$
3344	05668	$-12-(-3456+7)-(-8+9A)-B$	$BA+9*8*7*6-(-5+4+32)+1$
3345	05669	$12-(-3456+78+9*A-B)$	$-BA9+8*(7-6)-(-5-4321)$
3346	05670	$1-(2-3456)-(-7+8)-(-9+AB)$	$-BA9+8-(-7+6-(5+4321))$
3347	05671	$-12+3456+7-8-9-AB$	$-BA9-8-7-6*-5+4321$
3348	05672	$-12+3456+7*(-8-9)-(A+B)$	$-BA9-(-8-(7+6)-(-5+4321))$
3349	05673	$-12+3456-(7-8+9+AB)$	$BA+9*-8*7*6-5-43+21$
334A	05674	$1+2+3456-7-8-9-AB$	$-BA+9-(-8-76*54)-(-32-1)$
334B	05675	$-12+3456-7-8-(-9+AB)$	$B-A98-(76+5)*(-43-21)$
3350	05676	$-1+23*(-4+5*6*7)-(-8-9A)-B$	$B*-A9*(87-6-54-32+1)$
3351	05677	$-1234+5+6*(7+89A+B)$	$-BA9-8*7+65+4321$
3352	05678	$-12+3456-7-(8+9)-A*B$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6-5*(-4*3)^2+1)$
3353	05679	$-12+3456-7-89-A-B$	$-B+A+9-8*(-76-(5+432))-1$
3354	05680	$1*-2+3456-7-8-9A-B$	$B-A+9-(-87+65*4*3*-2+1)$
3355	05681	$1-(2-(3456-7-8)-(-9A-B))$	$-B+A-98-76*-54+3*2*1$
3356	05682	$-1-2-(-3456-7-(-8-9))-AB$	$-BA9+87-65+4321$
3357	05683	$-1-(-2-3456-(-7-8-9A))-B$	$BA+98+76*5*(4+3-2)*1$
3358	05684	$-12+3456-7-(-8-(-9A-B))$	$B+A+9*((8-7)^6+5^4+3)+2^1$
3359	05685	$1+2+3456-7-(8+9A+B)$	$-BA9-(8-7)-(6*-5-4321)$
335A	05686	$-1-2+3456-(-7+8-9+AB)$	$BA-9-8-7-65*4*-3*-2*-1$
335B	05687	$-12-(-3456-7)-(-8+9+AB)$	$B-(A9-8-(-76*-54+32))-1$
3360	05688	$1-(-2-3456)-(-7+8)-(-9+AB)$	$BA-9*-8+7+65*(-4+3*21)$
3361	05689	$-1+2*345*6+7-8-9A-B$	$B-A9-(-8+76*-54-32)+1$
3362	05690	$-12+3456-78-(9+AB)$	$-BA+9*8+76*54+3-2-1$
3363	05691	$-12+3456-(7-8)+9-AB$	$-B+A+9*-8*7*-6+5*(43-21)$
3364	05692	$1-(-2-3456+7)-8-(-9+AB)$	$-BA9+8*765+43*-21$
3365	05693	$1-2*3+4-(-5+6*7*8*-9-(-A+B))$	$B+A-(98-76*54)-(-3-21)$
3366	05694	$-1+2+3456-7-89-A-B$	$BA9-8*7+65*43+2*-1$
3367	05695	$1-2+3456+7-(8+9A)-B$	$-B-A*-9*-87+6*5*4*(32+1)$
3368	05696	$12-(-3456+7)-(-8+9A)-B$	$-BA+98-(76*-54+32*1)$
3369	05697	$-1*23*(-4-56-(-7+8)-(-9+AB))$	$-BA+98-76*-54-(32-1)$
336A	05698	$-12*(-3+4)*(5+6*-78+9+AB)$	$B-A-9*8+76*54+3*(2+1)$
336B	05699	$1+2-3+45*6*7+8*-9*(-A-B)$	$B-A9*8*-7+6+543*2*-1$
3370	05700	$-1*(2+34-5+6+7)*(8+9-AB)$	$-B-A-(9-8-76*54)-3*2*1$
3371	05701	$12+3456-7+8-9-AB$	$B+A*9-(8-76*54-3)+21$
3372	05702	$1-2-(-3456-7+8-9+AB)$	$B+A9-(8-7-654)*(3+2+1)$
3373	05703	$12+3456-7-8+9-AB$	$B-A+9+8-(76*54+3*21)$
3374	05704	$1-2-(-3456+7)+8-(-9+AB)$	$BA-9*-87*6*(-5+4)*(-3+2)*1$
3375	05705	$-12+3456-(-7-8)-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9-8+(-76-54)*-32+1$
3376	05706	$1+2+3456+7-8+9-AB$	$-BA+98-76*-54-3-21$
3377	05707	$1+2+3456-78-9-A-B$	$-B-A98-(76+5-4321)$
3378	05708	$-12+3456-78+9-A-B$	$B+A+9*8*7+6^5*4/3/2-1$
3379	05709	$1-(2-3456)-7-8-(-9*-A+B)$	$B*(A+9-8-7-6+54+321)$
337A	05710	$12-(-3456-7+8+9+AB)$	$B+A98-76*(5-43)+2+1$
337B	05711	$1-2+3456+7+8-(9A+B)$	$-BA9-8*-7-(6-5-4321)$
3380	05712	$12+3456-7-(-8+9A+B)$	$-B-A+9-(8-76*54)-3-21$
3381	05713	$-12+3456+7-89+A-B$	$-B+A9-876*-5-432-1$
3382	05714	$-1*2*(-3-456-7-89*(A+B))$	$-B-(-A9-876*5)+432*-1$
3383	05715	$-12+3456+7-(89+A-B)$	$-BA+9*-87*-6-5+4*-3*-21$
3384	05716	$-1*(-2-3456+7+89)*(-A+B)$	$BA9-8+7+65*(43+2-1)$
3385	05717	$-1-2-(-3456+7-8+9A-B)$	$-B-(A98+76)-(-5-4321)$
3386	05718	$12+3456-7-8-(9A-B)$	$-B+A-(98+76*-54-3*21)$
3387	05719	$12+3456-(-7-8)-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9*8-7*(-654-32)*1$
3388	05720	$1*-2+3456-78+9-A-B$	$-B-A-9-(8-7-6)*(-5+43)*21$
3389	05721	$-12+3456-7-89+A+B$	$B+A*-9+8*(-76+54-3)*-21$
338A	05722	$1+2+3456-(-7-8)*-9A+B$	$B-A-9-8+76*54+3-21$
338B	05723	$-1+2+3456-78+9-A-B$	$-B+A-(-9+8-(76*54-32+1))$
3390	05724	$-1*(2+3+4)*(567-(8+9AB))$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6+5+4^3)^2-1$
3391	05725	$-1-(-2-3456+78-(-9+A-B))$	$-B-(A98+7*(6+5))-4321$
3392	05726	$12*(345+6-78+9-(A-B))$	$B+A-9-8+76*54+3*2*-1$
3393	05727	$1-(-2-3456)-(-78+9+A+B)$	$-BA+98-76*-54-3*2-1$
3394	05728	$-12+3456-(78-9-(A-B))$	$-B+A9+(8-7*-6+5)*43*-2*-1$
3395	05729	$1+2+3456-78-(9-(-A+B))$	$-BA9-(-87-6*-5-4321)$
3396	05730	$-123+4+5-6*(-789+AB)$	$BA-9-(-876*5+432-1)$
3397	05731	$-1+23+45*(-6+789)-AB$	$B+A*(9+87-(6-5-4-321))$
3398	05732	$1-2*34*(-56-7)-(-8-9-A*-B)$	$-BA9-(8-(7+65))+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3399	05733	$1-2+3456+7+8-9A+B$	$-BA9-8-(-76+5)+4321$
339A	05734	$12+3456-(7-8)-(9A-B)$	$-BA9+8-7+65+4321$
339B	05735	$-12+3456+7-89-(-A-B)$	$B+A9-876^*-5-432-1$
33A0	05736	$-1^*-2^*(345+678+9AB)$	$-BA+98+76^*54-(-3+2)+1$
33A1	05737	$1+2^*(345+678+9AB)$	$-BA-98^*(7-(-6+54))-(-32-1)$
33A2	05738	$-1^*-2^*(34^*56-7-(-89-AB))$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7)-65^*(-43-21)$
33A3	05739	$12+3456-(78+9)^*(-A+B)$	$B-(A98+76)+5+4321$
33A4	05740	$-12^*(3-456-(7-89-AB))$	$B-A98-7-65+4321$
33A5	05741	$1-2-(-3456+78)-(-9-A+B)$	$BA9+87-65^*-43-2^*1$
33A6	05742	$-1-2-3+4^*(56-7^*8+9AB)$	$BA9-(-87-65^*43)-2+1$
33A7	05743	$-12-3-4^*-5^*6^*(-78-(-9-AB))$	$-BA9-8+76+5+4321$
33A8	05744	$-1+2-(3456-(78-9))^*(A-B)$	$BA9+87-65^*-43-(-2+1)$
33A9	05745	$-1+2-(-3456+78)-(-9+A-B)$	$BA+98+76^*(54-3)-(-2+1)$
33AA	05746	$-12+3456-7-8^*-9-AB$	$BA-(-9+876^*-5+432+1)$
33AB	05747	$1-2-(-3+45)+67^*-8^*-9+A^*B$	$BA-98-(-76^*54-(-32-1))$
33B0	05748	$12+3456+7+8-9A+B$	$-BA-9-87^*(6-54)+3^*-21$
33B1	05749	$1+2+3456-(78-(-9+A))^*+B$	$-BA9+8+76-5+4321$
33B2	05750	$-12+3456-78+9A+B$	$-B+A^*-9-8+7+65^*(43+21)$
33B3	05751	$-1-234+56^*78-(-9-A)-B$	$-BA-987-65+4321$
33B4	05752	$1-(-2-3456-7+89)-(-A-B)$	$-B-(A-9)+8+76^*54-(-3+2-1)$
33B5	05753	$1+2345+67^*8+9^*AB$	$-B-(-A+9-8-76^*54+3-2^*-1)$
33B6	05754	$-1-2+3456-(7-8+9)^*+A+B$	$B-A98+7-65+4321$
33B7	05755	$-12+3-45+67^*8^*9+AB$	$-B-A98-7^*6-(5-4321)$
33B8	05756	$12+3456-78+9A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*(7+6-(5+4)^3-2)^*1$
33B9	05757	$-1-2+3456-7+8^*9-AB$	$-BA9-87^*-65-(-4+321)$
33BA	05758	$12+3456-78+9-A+B$	$-BA9+87-6+5+4321$
33BB	05759	$1-(-2-3-456^*7-89A)-B$	$-BA9+8+76+5+4321$
3400	05760	$12+3456-78-(9-A)+B$	$-BA9+87+6-5+4321$
3401	05761	$-1-2+3456-(78-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9^*8+7^*6+5^*4^*3^*2+1$
3402	05762	$1-2-3-45-67^*-8^*9+AB$	$-BA-(-98-76^*54-(3+21))$
3403	05763	$12-(-3456-(7-(89-A)))^*+B$	$B+A+9^*(8-7+6+5^*4+3^*2)^*1$
3404	05764	$-1+2-(-3+45)-(67^*8^*-9-AB)$	$B-(-A+98-7)+65^*(43+21)$
3405	05765	$1+2-(-3456-(7-8^*9-(A-B)))$	$-B-A98-(7^*6-5)+4321$
3406	05766	$-12+3456-7^*8+9-A+B$	$-B+A-9+(-8+7+65)^*(43+21)$
3407	05767	$12+3456+7^*8-9A-B$	$-B+A-(98-7-6)^*(5+43)^*(-2+1)$
3408	05768	$-123-4-56^*-78-(9A+B)$	$-B-(A-9)-8+76^*54-(-3-21)$
3409	05769	$1-2^*(3+4)^*(5+6-7^*8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-876^*-5+4-321$
340A	05770	$1^*-2-3-456^*-7-(-89A-B)$	$-BA9+87+6+5+4321$
340B	05771	$12+34^*5-67^*8^*-9-AB$	$-BA+98-76^*-54+32-1$
3410	05772	$1^*(23+45-6)^*(7-8-9^*-A-B)$	$B-A^*-9^*8+7^*6^*-5^*4^*3^*-2+1$
3411	05773	$12+3+4^*(5-(-6+7))-(-8-9AB)$	$-BA-(-98+76^*-54)-(-32-1)$
3412	05774	$12+3456-7^*-8+9-AB$	$BA9+8^*-76^*-5+4+321$
3413	05775	$-1-2+3+456^*7-(-89A-B)$	$-B-A-(9-8-76^*54-32)-1$
3414	05776	$-1^*(-2+34)^*(5^*-6-(7+8))-(-9A-B)$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8-76^*54+32^*-1)$
3415	05777	$1-2+3456+78-9-AB$	$B-A98-7^*6-5+4321$
3416	05778	$-1^*-2^*-3^*(-4-5)^*(-6+7+89-A+B)$	$-B-A+9+8+76^*54-3+21$
3417	05779	$-1+23+456^*7+89A-B$	$-B-(A98+7-6^*5)+4321$
3418	05780	$-1-2^*3+(456-7+8)^*9^*(-A+B)$	$BA-(98+76^*-54-3^*2^*-1)$
3419	05781	$1+2-(-3456-78)-(9+AB)$	$B-A-9^*(87+6+5^*-4)+32^*1$
341A	05782	$-1-23-4-(5+67^*-8^*9)+AB$	$-B+A^*98-7-654^*(3^*-2+1)$
341B	05783	$1-2-(34-5+67^*-8^*9-AB)$	$B-A-(-9-8+76^*-54-3-2^*1)$
3420	05784	$1+2-(-3456+7)-(-8+9+A+B)$	$-B-A98-7-(6-(-5+4321))$
3421	05785	$-12+3456+78-9-A^*B$	$B+A+9-8+76^*54-3^*(-2+1)$
3422	05786	$-1+23-45^*6^*(-7-8)-9^*A^*-B$	$-B^*(A98+7-6^*5-432-1)$
3423	05787	$1^*-2-(-34+5)-6^*7^*(-8-9A-B)$	$B-(A98+7)-6^*5+4321$
3424	05788	$1-2-(-3456-78)-(9A+B)$	$-B-A9+(8-7+65)^*(43+21)$
3425	05789	$-12+3^*-45+(-67^*-8-9^*A)^*B$	$-BA9+87-(-6^*5-4321)$
3426	05790	$-1-2+3456-7+89-AB$	$BA+9^*-87^*-6+54-3+21$
3427	05791	$1+2^*345^*6+78+9-AB$	$BA-9^*8-76^*-54-(32+1)$
3428	05792	$1-2+3456-7+89-AB$	$B-A9+876^*5+4^*-3^*21$
3429	05793	$-12+3456+7-(-89+AB)$	$B-(A+9^*87^*-6+5^*-43)-21$
342A	05794	$-1-(-2-3456)-(7-89+AB)$	$-B+A9^*(-8-(-7-6))^*(5+4+3-2-1)$
342B	05795	$12+3456-7-8-9-A-B$	$B+A9-8^*76+5^*-43^*-21$
3430	05796	$12^*3^*(4-567+8^*9A-B)$	$BA9+8-7+65^*(43+2)+1$
3431	05797	$-1+2+3456-(-78-9+AB)$	$-B^*(A-9-8+76+5-(432+1))$
3432	05798	$-1-(2-3456+7)-(-8+9-(A-B))$	$-B-A98-(-7+6+5)+4321$
3433	05799	$1-(-2-3456-78)-(-9+AB)$	$BA+9-8^*(76-54-21)$
3434	05800	$-12+3456-7+89-A^*B$	$B-(-A+9-(-8-7^*-6^*(5-43))^*(-2-1))$
3435	05801	$12+3-456^*-7-8-9A^*-B$	$-BA+98^*-7-(-6-5)^*432+1$
3436	05802	$1+2+3456+78-9+A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7^*6^*5+4)^*3+2+1$
3437	05803	$12+3456+78-9A-B$	$B+A+9-8^*7+6^*5/4^*3-2-1$
3438	05804	$-1-(2-3456)-(-7-89)-AB$	$BA-9+87-654^*-3^*-2^*-1$
3439	05805	$-1^*(2-3456-(7+89-AB))$	$-B-(-A+9)-((8+76)^*-54+321)$
343A	05806	$-1-234+5^*(-67+8-9A^*-B)$	$-BA9+87^*(65-(4-3+2)-1)$
343B	05807	$12+3456-7-(-89+AB)$	$BA+9+8^*-7^*(-65+4-(3+21))$
3440	05808	$-1-2-(-3456-78+9A-B)$	$-B-A98+7-6+5+4321$
3441	05809	$-12-(-3456+7)-(-8+9-(A+B))$	$B+A+9^*(-8-(-7-6^*5)+432)+1$
3442	05810	$12+3456+78+9-AB$	$-B-A98+7-(-6+5)+4321$
3443	05811	$-1-2+3+(-4-56)^*(-78+9)-A+B$	$B+A^*(98-(7-654+321))$
3444	05812	$-1+2-(-3456-78)-(-9A+B)$	$B+A9+87+654^*-3^*-2+1$
3445	05813	$12+3456+78-9A^*-B$	$BA-9-8^*(-76-5-432-1)$
3446	05814	$-1-(-23+4^*5)-6^*(-7+89-A)^*-B$	$-B+A+9+8-76^*-54+32^*1$
3447	05815	$12+3456-7-8-9A-B$	$-B-A+9-8+76^*54+3^*21$
3448	05816	$1+2+3456+7-8+9-A-B$	$B-A98-(7+6)-(-5-4321)$
3449	05817	$-1^*(2-3456+7)-8+9+A-B$	$B-A98-(7+(6-5)^*-4321)$
344A	05818	$-1-2+3456-7-8+9-A+B$	$B-A98-7-(-6+5-4321)$
344B	05819	$1^*2+3456+78-9^*A-B$	$-B^*(-A-9+8+76+5-432+1)$
3450	05820	$1+2+3456+78+9-A^*B$	$B-A98-(-7+6-(-5+4321))$
3451	05821	$-12+3456+7-(8-9+A-B)$	$-BA+987^*6-54^*32+1$
3452	05822	$-1+2+3456-(7+8)-(-9+A-B)$	$-BA^*(-98-7+6^*5-(-43-2+1))$
3453	05823	$-12+3456+7-8-9A+B$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8+7-65^*(43+21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3454	05824	$-1*(2-34+56)*(7-89-A*B)$	$BA-98-76^*-54+32^*1$
3455	05825	$12+3456+78-9A+B$	$BA-(98+76^*-54)-(-32-1)$
3456	05826	$1+2+3456-(7+8+9-(A+B))$	$BA-9^*8^*-76-(543+21)$
3457	05827	$-12+3456-(78-9A+B)$	$-BA+98765-4321$
3458	05828	$1+2-3+4-(-5-67^*8^*9-AB)$	$B-A98-7+6+5+4321$
3459	05829	$12-(-3456-(7-8))-(-9-A+B)$	$-BA-(987-6-(-5+4321))$
345A	05830	$-1+2^*-3^*(-456-78)+9AB$	$B-A98-(-7+6)+5+4321$
345B	05831	$-12+3456-7-89+AB$	$-BA+98^*(-7+654-(3-21))$
3460	05832	$-1+2+3-(-4-5)+67^*8^*9+AB$	$B+A-9-8-7+6^{\wedge}5/4^*3+2+1$
3461	05833	$12+3456-(7+8-9-A)-B$	$BA9-87^*(6-5-4-32+1)$
3462	05834	$-1+23^*-4-56^*-78-(9A+B)$	$B-A9-87^*(6-54)-(-3+21)$
3463	05835	$-1+2^*3+45^*(6+78-9A+B)$	$B-A-9+8-(-76^*54-3^*21)$
3464	05836	$123-456^*-7-8-9^*-AB$	$-BA9-(-87-65-4321)$
3465	05837	$-12+3456+7+8+9-A+B$	$-B-(A9+87^*(6-54))-3^*(-2+1)$
3466	05838	$-1+2+3456-(-7-(-8-9))+A+B$	$-B+A+98-(-76^*54+32-1)$
3467	05839	$123-4^*5-67^*-8^*-9^*(A-B)$	$-BA-987+6+5+4321$
3468	05840	$1-(2-3456)-(78-9A+B)$	$B+A-9-8+7+6^{\wedge}5/4^*3-2-1$
3469	05841	$-12-(-3456-7-(-8+9))-(-A-B)$	$B^*(A+9-87+(-6+5)^*-432+1)$
346A	05842	$1+2-(-3456-78)-(9^*A-B)$	$B-A98+7+6+5+4321$
346B	05843	$12+3456+7+8+9-A-B$	$-B+A98-7^*(-6+5-432+1)$
3470	05844	$-1+2^*-3+45-67^*-8^*9-A^*-B$	$BA9-8+76^*(-5+43)-2+1$
3471	05845	$12+3456+7-(-8+9)-(-A+B)$	$BA-9+8^*-7^*-6^*(5+4^*3)^*(2-1)$
3472	05846	$-1-2-(-3456-7)-(-8-9-A)-B$	$BA-9-(8-76^*54+32+1)$
3473	05847	$12+3456+7+8-9-A+B$	$B-A98-(7-6^*5-4321)$
3474	05848	$12+3456+7-(-8-9)^*-A+B$	$-B+A9-(8-76^*54)-(-3+21)$
3475	05849	$-12+3456-78+9A+B$	$-B-A^*(-98-765+432+1)$
3476	05850	$-1+2-(-3456-(7+8+9))-(-A+B)$	$-B-A^*98-7^*(-654+3^*-21)$
3477	05851	$1-2+3456+7+8+(9-A)^*-B$	$-B-A+98-(76^*-54+3+2-1)$
3478	05852	$12^*(-345-67-8-9^*A^*-B)$	$B^*(-A-9)^*(-8-7+6-(5-4+32^*-1))$
3479	05853	$12+3456+78-(9^*A-B)$	$B+A+9^*8+76^*54+3-2-1$
347A	05854	$1-2+3456+7-8+9+A+B$	$BA+9^*-8^*-76-(543-2-1)$
347B	05855	$12+3456-78+9A-B$	$-BA+9^*8^*7^*(6+5)-4+321$
3480	05856	$1-234-567^*-8-(-9-A)^*-B$	$-B-(A9-87^*(-6+54)+3-21)$
3481	05857	$-1+2+3456-78-9+AB$	$-B+A98+765^*4-3-21$
3482	05858	$1-2+3456-(-7+89-AB)$	$-BA-987-6^*-5+4321$
3483	05859	$12+3456-(7-(-89+AB))$	$B+A+98-76^*-54-32^*1$
3484	05860	$-12+3456-78-(-9-AB)$	$BA9-8-(-7^*6+(-5-4)^*321)$
3485	05861	$-123+4^*(-5-6+78+9AB)$	$B-(A98-7-(6^*5+4321))$
3486	05862	$1+2+3456+7-(89-AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+6^{\wedge}5/4^*3-2+1$
3487	05863	$12+3456+7+8-(-9-A+B)$	$BA9+8+76^*(-5+43)+2^*1$
3488	05864	$-1+2-(-3456+78-9A-B)$	$B+A+9-8+7+6^{\wedge}5/4^*3+2+1$
3489	05865	$-1-234+56^*78-9+AB$	$BA+9-8+76^*54+32^*-1$
348A	05866	$1-(-2-3456+78-9A-B)$	$BA+9-8+76^*54-32+1$
348B	05867	$12+3456+7+8-9+AB$	$B+A+9-(-8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)^*3+2^*1$
3490	05868	$-1-2+3456+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A98-765^*-4-32-1$
3491	05869	$12+3456+7-(-8-9-A)+B$	$-B-A^*(-98-(765-(432-1)))$
3492	05870	$-1^*(-2-3)^*(-4-56+789+AB)$	$B+A9-(-8-76^*54)-32^*1$
3493	05871	$12+3456-(7-8-9)+A+B$	$B-(-A9-(8-76^*-54))-(-32-1)$
3494	05872	$-1-(-2-3456)-(-7-8-9-A-B)$	$-B-A-(987+65)+4321$
3495	05873	$12+3456+7-(89-AB)$	$B+A+9-(-8-(76^*54-3^*-21))$
3496	05874	$-12-(-3456-78)-(9+A+B)$	$-B+A+98-(-76^*-54^*(-3+2)+1)$
3497	05875	$-1+2-(-3456+78)+9+AB$	$-B+A+(987+6+54)^*(3+2-1)$
3498	05876	$-1^*(-2-3456-(-78+9+AB))$	$B-A-(-98+76^*-54^*(3-2))-1$
3499	05877	$12+3456-(78-9A)+B$	$-B+A+98-76^*-54+3-(2-1)$
349A	05878	$-1-234+5^*678+9AB$	$BA-(9+8+76^*-54)-(-3^*-2+1)$
349B	05879	$-1+2-(-3456+7+8^*9-AB)$	$B+A98-765^*-4-3-21$
34A0	05880	$-1^*(-2-3456+7+8^*9-AB)$	$B-A-(-9-87^*(-6+54+3+2))-1$
34A1	05881	$1+2+3456-(7+8^*9-AB)$	$BA-(-9-(8-76^*-54+32^*-1))$
34A2	05882	$-1+23+4^*(56+7^*8)^*(-9+A+B)$	$-B-(-A9-8)+76^*54-(3+2)+1$
34A3	05883	$-1-(234-56^*78)-(-9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)^*-3^*(2-1)$
34A4	05884	$1+23+45^*(-6+78)+9A^*B$	$-B+A98-765^*-4^*(3-2)-1$
34A5	05885	$-1-2-(-3456-(78-9))-(-A-B)$	$BA-9-8+76^*54-3+2+1$
34A6	05886	$-1+2345+678+9^*A^*B$	$-B-(A98-7)-(-65-4321)$
34A7	05887	$-1-2-(-3456-7^*8)+9-(-A+B)$	$-B-A98-(-76+5-4321)$
34A8	05888	$12+3456-78-(-9-AB)$	$BA-9-8^*-7^*-6-5^*43^*-21$
34A9	05889	$-12-34+56^*78-9A-B$	$-BA+987-6^*(-543-2+1)$
34AA	05890	$-1-2^*3^*(-4-5-678)-9^*-A+B$	$BA-9+876^*5-(-4+321)$
34AB	05891	$1-(-2-3456-78-(-9-A)+B)$	$-BA-(9-876)-54^*3^*-21$
34B0	05892	$12-(-3456+7+8^*9)+AB$	$-B+A-(987+65)+4321$
34B1	05893	$1-(-2-3456-(-7-8-(-9^*A+B)))$	$B+A+9+8-(-7-6^{\wedge}5/4)^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
34B2	05894	$-12-(-3456-78+9-A)-B$	$B-A98-7+65+4321$
34B3	05895	$1+2+3456+7-(8^*9-AB)$	$BA9+87^*-6+54^*-3^*-21$
34B4	05896	$1+2-3-4+5^*(-67+89A-B)$	$B^*(A-9-(8-7)-65-(-432+1))$
34B5	05897	$1+2-345-((-67+8)^*-9^*-A+B)$	$BA9+87+65^*(43+2)^*1$
34B6	05898	$-12+3456-(7+8)-(-9^*A-B)$	$B+A9-(8+76^*-54)+3^*2^*1$
34B7	05899	$1+2^*3^*-45-6^*7^*(-8-9-AB)$	$-BA-9^*(87-6-543)-21$
34B8	05900	$-1-2+3456-7-(-89+A+B)$	$B+A9+(-8-7)^*(65-(4+321))$
34B9	05901	$-1-(23-456^*7)+8+9AB$	$B+A9+8-(76^*-54-3^*-2)-1$
34BA	05902	$1+234-5+67^*-8^*-9-A^*B$	$-B-A9+876+54^*-3^*-21$
34BB	05903	$-123-4-5^*-678+9A^*B$	$B+A-(-98-76^*54)-3^*2^*-1$
3500	05904	$-12-(-3456+7+8-9A+B)$	$-BA+9876-5^*-43^*21$
3501	05905	$123+4+(5-6+7)^*(8^*9A+B)$	$-BA-987+65+4321$
3502	05906	$12+3456+7-(8^*9-AB)$	$-BA+9+8+76^*(54+3)+2-1$
3503	05907	$-1-(2+3+456^*-7+8-9AB)$	$-B-(A9-8-7^*654+321)$
3504	05908	$1+23+456^*7+(-8-9A)^*-B$	$B-A98+7+65+4321$
3505	05909	$-12+3456-7+89+A-B$	$B-(A98-76+5-4321)$
3506	05910	$12+3-(-4+56)^*-78+9^*(A+B)$	$-B-A9^*8+7^*654+321$
3507	05911	$-12-(-3456+7)-(-89+A-B)$	$B+A^*(-98-76-(-543-21))$
3508	05912	$-12+3456+78+9A-B$	$B-(A+98+76^*(-54-3))-(-2+1)$
3509	05913	$-12-3456^*(7-8)-9^*-A+B$	$B-A9-(8-7^*654)-321$
350A	05914	$-12+3456-(-78-9)-A+B$	$B-(-A+987)-(65-4321)$

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350B	05915	$1-2+3-456^*-7-8+9AB$	$-B+A^*(9+87+6)^*5+43-21$
3510	05916	$-12-(-3456+7+8)-(-9+A^*-B)$	$B-(A-98+76^*-54-32)+1$
3511	05917	$12-345^*6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$-B-A9+876^*5+4^*-32-1$
3512	05918	$-12+3456+7-8+9A-B$	$-B^*(A-(9+8)+7-(-65-(-432-1)))$
3513	05919	$-1+2345-6^*-78+9AB$	$B-A98-(-76-5)+4321$
3514	05920	$1-(-2-3456)+7-(-89A+B)$	$B-A+9+876^*5+4^*-3^*21$
3515	05921	$1-(-2-3456+7+8-9A+B)$	$B-A9+8^*-7^*6+5^*-43^*-21$
3516	05922	$1-2-(-3456+7)-(-89-A+B)$	$B+A9-(-8-76)^*(5+43+2+1)$
3517	05923	$-12+3456+7+89A-B$	$BA-9+8+76^*54-3+21$
3518	05924	$12+3456+78-9-A+B$	$B-A9+876+54^*3^*21$
3519	05925	$-1-2+3456+78+9-(A-B)$	$-B+A-(9+87^*(6-54))-(-32+1)$
351A	05926	$-12+3456-7-(8-(9A+B))$	$BA9+8^*-76^*-5+432-1$
351B	05927	$-1+2+3456+7-8-9^*-A+B$	$BA9+8^*-76^*-5-432^*-1$
3520	05928	$-1-2+3^*(456-78+9AB)$	$BA9-8^*76^*-5+432+1$
3521	05929	$-1-2+3456+7-(8-(9A-B))$	$BA-9+8-76^*-54-(-3-21)$
3522	05930	$1^*-2+3456+7-8-(-9A+B)$	$B+A9^*87+6-5-4321$
3523	05931	$-12-(-3456+7)-(-89-A-B)$	$B+A+9^*8+7+6^*5/4^*3-2+1$
3524	05932	$12+3456-7-(8-9A+B)$	$B-A9^*8+7^*654+321$
3525	05933	$1-(2-3456+7-8-9A+B)$	$B-A9^*-8+76+54^*3^*21$
3526	05934	$-1-2-(-3456-7-89-A+B)$	$-B-A-9^*87^*-6-54+321$
3527	05935	$-12+3456-7+8-9+A+B$	$B+A98-765^*-4+3+21$
3528	05936	$1-(-2-3456-(-7-8-9))+AB$	$BA9-87^*(-6+5)^*(4+32-1)$
3529	05937	$-12+3456-7-(8-9-AB)$	$-BA+987+6^*5^*-4^*(-32-1)$
352A	05938	$-12-3-456+7^*8^*9A-B$	$-B-A-987-6-5+4321$
352B	05939	$1-2+3456-(7+8)+9A+B$	$-BA+987^*6-543^*(2+1)$
3530	05940	$12+3456+78+9A-B$	$B^*A^*9^*(8-(-76+54))-(-3+21)$
3531	05941	$12+34-5-6^*(-789+AB)$	$-B-A-987^*-6+54^*32^*-1$
3532	05942	$12+3456-(-78-9)-(A-B)$	$BA-98^*(-7-6+5-4+32^*-1)$
3533	05943	$1+2-(-3456-(-7-8+9A)-B)$	$-B-A+9+87+65^*(43+21)$
3534	05944	$12+3456+78-9A+B$	$B-A9-8^*(7+6-543)-2^*1$
3535	05945	$-12-3^*4+56^*78-9^*A-B$	$B+A9+8-76^*-54-(-32+1)$
3536	05946	$-12+3456+7+8+9-A^*-B$	$-B-A-9^*(87-(-6+543+2)+1)$
3537	05947	$1-2-(-3456-78-9-A)+B$	$B+A9^*8-(7+6-5)^*(-432+1)$
3538	05948	$-1-(2-3456+7+8-9)+AB$	$-B-A-987-6+5+4321$
3539	05949	$-1+2+3456+7-(-8-9A)-B$	$B-A9-8^*(7+6-543)+2+1$
353A	05950	$1-2+3456-7-8+9+AB$	$-B-(A+987-(6-5))+4321$
353B	05951	$-12+3456+7-8+9+AB$	$B+A^*9^*-8^*-7-(-654+3+21)$
3540	05952	$1-(-2-3456-(-7+8))-(-9+AB))$	$B+A+98^*-7+(6+5)^*(432-1)$
3541	05953	$12-(-3456-7-89+A-B)$	$-B+A^*-9^*8^*-7+654-3-2+1$
3542	05954	$-1-2+3+4-56^*-78+9-AB$	$-BA9+87^*(6+54)+321$
3543	05955	$-1+234^*5+6^*(7+89A-B)$	$B+A9+(8+76)^*54-321$
3544	05956	$-12+3456+7+8+9A+B$	$B+A-9+8^*(7+6+(5+4)^3+2-1)$
3545	05957	$-1^*(234+567^*-8+9A-B)$	$-B+A^*9^*-8^*-7-(-654-3)-(2+1)$
3546	05958	$1-(-23-4)-(56+7^*-8^*(9A-B))$	$-B+A+987+6^*5^*4^*32^*1$
3547	05959	$12+3456-7-(-89-A-B)$	$-BA-98+76^*54+321$
3548	05960	$-1+2345^*6-(-7-8)^*9^*-AB$	$-B+A9-8-76^*(54+3-2)^*-1$
3549	05961	$-1+2+3456-(-7-8-(9-A^*-B))$	$-B+A-(987^*-6+54^*-32^*-1)$
354A	05962	$12+3456+7+8-(-9A+B)$	$-B^*(A9-8+76-5^*4^*-3)^*2^*-1$
354B	05963	$1^*-2+3456+7-8+9+AB$	$B+A^*-9+876-54^*3^*-21$
3550	05964	$12-3^*-4^*5^*6+7+(8-9A)^*-B$	$-BA^*(98-76-(54+3)-2+1)$
3551	05965	$12+3456-7-8-(-9-AB)$	$B-A-98^*7+65^*4^*(-3+21)$
3552	05966	$1-2-(-3456+7-8-9-AB)$	$B+A^*-9-(-8-7)^*(6^*(-5-4)+321)$
3553	05967	$-12+3456-(-7-8-9-AB)$	$B+A+9+8+((-7-6)^*5-4^*3)^2+1$
3554	05968	$1+2-(-3456-7+8-9-AB)$	$B-A+9^*-8+7^*654-321$
3555	05969	$1-2+3456+7+8+9A+B$	$-B-(-A+987-(6-5)^*4321)$
3556	05970	$12+3456-7+8-(-9A-B)$	$B-A-987-(6-5)+4321$
3557	05971	$1^*-2345-6^*-7^*(89+AB)$	$-BA-9-876-5+4321$
3558	05972	$12+3-4-5^*-678-9^*-AB$	$B-A-987+6-5+4321$
3559	05973	$12+3456-(-7-89)-(-A-B)$	$B^*(-A9-8-76+543-2+1)$
355A	05974	$-1-2-3^*-4-56^*-78-9A+B$	$-B+A+98+7-65^*(-43-21)$
355B	05975	$-12+3456+7^*8-(-9A+B)$	$BA9+8^*-7^*65-43+2-1$
3560	05976	$-123+4-(-5-6^*(-78-(-9+A)))^*-B)$	$BA-(9-8+76^*-54)-3^*-21$
3561	05977	$-1-23^*(-45+6-7^*8-9A)+B$	$B+A9-8-(7+65^*(-43-21))$
3562	05978	$12-(-3+4)-(56^*-78+9A)+B$	$BA+9-(8-76^*54)-3^*-21$
3563	05979	$-1+2+34+(5+67)^*8^*9-A^*B$	$-B-A-987+6^*5+4321$
3564	05980	$-1+23+4-(-56^*78-9)-AB$	$-BA-9+8^*7-(65+4)^*-3^*21$
3565	05981	$-1+23-(456+7^*-8^*9A+B)$	$BA-(-98-76^*54)-(-32-1)$
3566	05982	$-1+2+3456+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9-876-5+4321$
3567	05983	$-12+3456+78+9^*A-B$	$BA9+8^*7^*65-(4-32^*-1)$
3568	05984	$12+3456+7+8+9A+B$	$-B+A9^*87-(-65+4321)$
3569	05985	$-1-2345-6-7^*(8-9AB)$	$BA9-8^*(-7-6-54-321)$
356A	05986	$12-(-3-4)-56^*-78-(9A-B)$	$B+A+(9+8^*(7+6^*5)^4)^*(3+2)^*1$
356B	05987	$1^*-23+4-5^*(67-89A-B)$	$-BA-987^*-6+5^*(4-321)$
3570	05988	$12+3456-(-7-8^*(9+A)+B)$	$-BA-9^*-8-(7+6)^*(-5-4-321)$
3571	05989	$1-(2-(-3+4^*5)^*6)+(-7-8)^*9+9A-B$	$-BA+9-876-5+4321$
3572	05990	$1-(-23+4)+5^*(-67+89A)+B$	$BA9+8^*7^*65+4-32-1$
3573	05991	$123-4+5+67^*8^*9+AB$	$B+A^*-98+(7-65)^*-43^*2^*1$
3574	05992	$1+2-(-3456-7^*8)-(-9A+B)$	$-B-A9-876+5+4321$
3575	05993	$1^*2+345^*-6-7^*-89A+B$	$B-(-A9-8+7)+65^*(43+21)$
3576	05994	$-1-(-2345-67^*(-89+AB))$	$-B-A9-876^*-5-43-21$
3577	05995	$1234+5^*6^*78+9^*AB$	$-B^*(A+9-8-76-5-4-321)$
3578	05996	$1+2345-67^*(89-AB)$	$B+A-(-98-7+65^*(-43-21))$
3579	05997	$-12+34-56^*-78-9^*A-B$	$-B-(A+9^*87^*-6+5-4)+321$
357A	05998	$1-2+34+5^*678-9^*-AB$	$B+A^*-9-87^*(-65-4-3+21)$
357B	05999	$-1+2345-67^*-8+9AB$	$-BA+9-876-(-5-4321)$
3580	06000	$-1+2^*3+(45-6^*(-7+89)-A)^*-B$	$B-(-A-9+87^*(6-54)+3-(-2+1))$
3581	06001	$1+2345-67^*-8+9AB$	$-B-A-(9^*8^*-76-(-5+4-321))$
3582	06002	$-1^*(2345-67^*(8+9A)+B)$	$B+A-987+6-(-5-4321)$
3583	06003	$1-2^*34-56^*-78+9-A+B$	$-B-A+987+6^*543-2+1$
3584	06004	$-1+23^*4+5-6^*(-789+AB)$	$B-A9-(876-(-5+4321))$
3585	06005	$1^*(-2-3)^*(-4+5+67-89A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9+8+76^*(-54-3))-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3586	06006	$1^* - 2^* - 3^*(45+678-9-(A-B))$	$BA9-8-765^*-4-32-1$
3587	06007	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5+(-6-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA-9+876^*5-43-(2-1)$
3588	06008	$-12-(-3456+7)-(8^*-9-AB)$	$B+A-9^*((-8-7)^*-6+5)^*(-4-3)+2/1$
3589	06009	$1+2+(-3+4^{\wedge}5)^*6-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A+9^*87^*-6+5+4-321)$
358A	06010	$-1-2+3+4-56^*(-7-(89-A)+B)$	$B+A9+87^*(-6+54-3+2)-1$
358B	06011	$12+3456+78-(9^*-A+B)$	$-B+A9^*(-8^*7^*(-6-5)-(-43-2+1))$
3590	06012	$-1^*(-2+3)^*4^*(-5-67+8-9AB)$	$BA+98-76^*54-3-(2+1)$
3591	06013	$1+2^*3-4+5^*(-67+89A+B)$	$BA+98+76^*54-3+2^*-1$
3592	06014	$1-2345+67^*(89+A+B)$	$B-A9-876+5+4321$
3593	06015	$-1+23^*-4^*-56-789-A+B$	$B+A+9^*(8+7^*6+5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
3594	06016	$-1-23-4567+89^*AB$	$-B-A9-876^*-5-(43+2+1)$
3595	06017	$-1^*(23+4567-89^*AB)$	$BA9-(8-765^*4)-(-3+21)$
3596	06018	$1-23-4567-89^*-AB$	$BA+98-76^*54^*(3-2)^*1$
3597	06019	$12+345-6^*-78^*(9-A+B)$	$BA9+8+7^*(6-5+432-1)$
3598	06020	$-12+3456-7+89+A^*B$	$BA9-(-876+5^*(-432+1))$
3599	06021	$-1^*(-23-456)^*(-78-9^*-A+B)$	$B+A+987+6^*543-21$
359A	06022	$-1-2+3456+78-(-9A+B)$	$-B-(A9+876^*-5+43-2-1)$
359B	06023	$-1+2+3456-7-(-8^*9-AB)$	$BA9+8+765^*4-32^*1$
35A0	06024	$1-(2-3456-78)-(-9A+B)$	$BA-(-98-76^*54)+3-(-2-1)$
35A1	06025	$-1^*(-2+3+4)^*(-5+6+78+9A^*-B)$	$BA9+876-5^*432^*-1$
35A2	06026	$-123-45^*67-8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA-98-765+4321$
35A3	06027	$-12-34+56^*78-9^*(A-B)$	$-B-A-9-876^*-5-43^*(2+1)$
35A4	06028	$1-(-2-3456-78-9A)-B$	$-B^*(A+9-87-6-5+4-321)$
35A5	06029	$-12-3+4-56^*-78-9-A-B$	$B-A+9-87^*6^*(-5-4)+321$
35A6	06030	$12+3456-7-(-8+9^*(A-B))$	$-B-A98+765^*(4+3)-2^*-1$
35A7	06031	$1^*(-2-(-34-5)-6)^*(7^*8-(-9A+B))$	$BA9-8+7^*6^*(-54-32-1)$
35A8	06032	$1-23-4-56^*-78-(9-A+B)$	$B-(A-987)+6^*(543-(-2+1))$
35A9	06033	$-12-(-3+4567)+89^*AB$	$-BA-9+876^*5-(4-3+21)$
35AA	06034	$12^*(345-(6-78)-(9+AB))$	$B-A-9+876+54^*3^*21$
35AB	06035	$12+3-4+5^*6-7^*8^*(-9A+B)$	$-BA9+8+76^*(54-3+21)$
35B0	06036	$12+3456-(7^*-8-9-AB)$	$B+A+(9+8^*7)^*6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}2^*1$
35B1	06037	$-1-2+3456+78-9+AB$	$-B+A-9+8+7^*654-321$
35B2	06038	$-1-(2+3)-4567+89^*AB$	$-BA+9^*(87+6)^*5+43^*21$
35B3	06039	$1-2+3456+78-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A^*-98+76+54^*-3^*-21$
35B4	06040	$1-(-2-3456)-(-78-9+A^*-B)$	$B-(A9-876^*5)-(-43+2-1)$
35B5	06041	$-1-(-2-3456-78)-9+AB$	$BA9-8^*-7^*65+4^*(3+2-1)$
35B6	06042	$-1^*(-2-(3456+78)-(-9+AB))$	$B-A9+876^*5-43+2-1$
35B7	06043	$-1-2+3456-(7-8-(9+A))^*B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*654-321$
35B8	06044	$-12+3456+78+9+AB$	$B+A+987-6^*-543+2^*-1$
35B9	06045	$1+2-(34+56^*-78-(9-A)-B)$	$BA9-8-765^*-4^*(3+2^*-1)$
35BA	06046	$-1-(-2345-6)-(-7-8)^*(9+AB)$	$-B+A-987+65+4321$
35BB	06047	$-1-2+34-5^*(67-89A-B)$	$BA9+8+7^*6^*(-54-32-1)$
3600	06048	$-1+2+3-4567-89^*-AB$	$B-A-987+65+4321$
3601	06049	$123+4+5-6^*(-7+89)^*-A-B$	$B-A-(9-(-876^*-5+4^*-32-1))$
3602	06050	$1+2-(-3456-78-(9A+B))$	$-B^*A^*(-9+8-(76-54+3)-21)$
3603	06051	$12+3456+78+9+A^*B$	$-BA-(-987+6+54^*-3^*21)$
3604	06052	$-1-2+3456-(7-89-AB)$	$-BA+9-876^*-5+(4-3)^*-21$
3605	06053	$1-23-4+56^*78+(-9+A)^*B$	$B+A-(9-8+76^*(-54-3)-2-1)$
3606	06054	$12+3456+78-9+AB$	$B+A-9+876-54^*-3^*21$
3607	06055	$12-3-4567+89^*AB$	$-B+A9-87^*(6-54)-32+1$
3608	06056	$-1-23+4-56^*-78-(-9-A+B)$	$B+A+(9^*8+7+6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}1$
3609	06057	$-1^*(-2-3456+7-89-AB)$	$-BA+98+7^*(6-5)^*(-4+3^*-21)$
360A	06058	$1+2+3456-7+89+AB$	$-BA-9-(8-76^*54-321)$
360B	06059	$-1+2-(-3456-78)-(-9-AB)$	$B-A9+876^*5-(-4+32-1)$
3610	06060	$-1-2+3-(4-(-56+7)^*-89)-AB$	$-BA-(9+876^*-5+4-3-2^*1)$
3611	06061	$12+3456+78+9A+B$	$-BA+9^*(8-76+543)+2^*1$
3612	06062	$123+4-5+6^*(789-AB)$	$BA9-(-8+765^*-4-3+2^*1)$
3613	06063	$-1-(-2+345+6^*-789+AB)$	$-BA+987+6+54^*3^*21$
3614	06064	$-123-(45-6^*(-7+8-9)^*-AB)$	$-BA+9-876^*-5-4^*-3-21$
3615	06065	$12+3-4^*(5+67)^*(-8-9A-B)$	$BA-98-7^*-654-321$
3616	06066	$-1-2+3456-(-7-89)+AB$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*76+54-321$
3617	06067	$1+2-3-(-4-(-56^*-78+9^*(A-B)))$	$BA9+8+765^*4+3+2+1$
3618	06068	$1-2+3456+7+89+AB$	$B+A-987-(-65-4321)$
3619	06069	$12+3456-(7-89-AB)$	$B-A9+876^*5+4^*-3^*2+1$
361A	06070	$-1+2+3456+7+89+AB$	$-BA-9^*8-(765-4321)$
361B	06071	$1^*2+3456+7-(-89-AB)$	$-BA-9^*8-76+5^*-43^*-21$
3620	06072	$12+3456-(-78-(9+AB))$	$B-A-(-9-876^*5)+4^*(-32+1)$
3621	06073	$1+2^*(34+567)^*(-8-9+A+B)$	$BA+98^*7+(-6-5)^*(-432+1)$
3622	06074	$-1+23^*(4+56+7)-(-8-(9+AB)))$	$-BA-(9-876^*5-4^*3-2-1)$
3623	06075	$1+2+3^*4+56^*78+9-A-B$	$-BA-9^*8^*(-7-(65-4))+321$
3624	06076	$-1^*(-2345-(678-9^*-AB))$	$B-A+9^*(-8-76+543+2)^*1$
3625	06077	$1-(-2345-678-9^*AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7^*-654-321$
3626	06078	$-12+3456-(-7-8)^*9+AB$	$BA9+87^*6^*5-43^*-21$
3627	06079	$1^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5^*6+7-8^*9A-B$	$B-A+9+876^*5+4^*3-21$
3628	06080	$-1-(2+345+6^*-789)+A^*-B$	$-B-(A-(-98+76^*54+321))$
3629	06081	$12-345+6^*(789-A-B)$	$BA-98+76^*(54+3)+21$
362A	06082	$1+2+(34-(5+6))^*(78+9A)-B$	$BA-987-6^*5+4321$
362B	06083	$12-(-3456-7)-(-89-AB)$	$BA9+8-(-765^*4+3)+21$
3630	06084	$1-2+3+4-5^*-678+9A^*B$	$B-A+9^*87^*-6+54+321$
3631	06085	$-123-(-4+567^*-8)-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9-(-8-76^*54)+321$
3632	06086	$-1-2^*-34^*5+67^*8^*9A-B$	$-B-A9^*-8^*7+6^*-54^*3+21$
3633	06087	$1+2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^*8-9+A-B$	$-BA-9+8-7^*(-654+32^*1)$
3634	06088	$-123-4567-89A^*-B$	$-BA+9^*-8^*7^*6-5432^*-1$
3635	06089	$-12-3+4+56^*78+9A+B$	$B-A9+876^*5-4+(-3+2)^*-1$
3636	06090	$12^*(3+456-7+8^*-9-AB)$	$-BA+9-876^*-5-4^*3+21$
3637	06091	$12+3-4-5^*-678+9A^*B$	$B-A9-(8+76^*-54)+321$
3638	06092	$-1-23+4^*(5+6-(-78-9AB))$	$-B-A-9-876-(5-4321)$
3639	06093	$-1-234+567^*8+9A+B$	$BA+98+76^*54+3^*21$
363A	06094	$1-2+3^*4^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8^*9A-B$	$-B+A+9^*8^*(76+5-4)-321$
363B	06095	$-123-4-567^*-8-(-9+AB)$	$B-A9+876^*5-(-4+3)^*2+1$
3640	06096	$12+34+56^*78-9-A-B$	$BA+98+7^*6^*(54+3^*21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3641	06097	$12-345-6^*-789+A^*-B$	$BA9-8^*(-76-5+4-321)$
3642	06098	$1-2+3+4^*5^*6-7^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A9+8+7^*(654+32^*-1)$
3643	06099	$-1^*(23-(-4-5-6-(7+8)))^*(-9A+B)$	$-B+A^*98+76^*(5+43-(2-1))$
3644	06100	$1-2+3+4+56^*78^*(-9+A)-B$	$-B-A-(-98+76^*(-54-3))-21$
3645	06101	$123+4-(56+7^*-8^*(9A-B))$	$BA-(987+6+5-4321)$
3646	06102	$-1^*(2-(-3+45)-6)^*(7-(-89+A-B))$	$-B-A-9-876+5+4321$
3647	06103	$-123+4-567^*-8+9-AB$	$-B+A^*-98-76-5+4321$
3648	06104	$12^*(-34+5-678+9AB)$	$-BA-98-7-6+5^*-43^*-21$
3649	06105	$-123+4567-(8+9AB)$	$B^*(-A-(-9-8-(76+5)))-(4-321))$
364A	06106	$-1-2+3+4-56^*-78+9+A+B$	$-BA^*(9-87+65-43+21)$
364B	06107	$123+4+56^*78-9-AB$	$-B+A^*(9-87^*-6-5)-43^*-2^*-1$
3650	06108	$-1+2+3+4+56+78+9^*(A+B)$	$B-A^*(-98-7^*65)-(-4+321)$
3651	06109	$1-(-2+3+45)-(-6+7^*8^*-9A)-B$	$BA-9+8^*(-7-6-5^*-4^*32^*1)$
3652	06110	$123-4-56^*-78-9A-B$	$-B-(A-9)-(876+5-4321)$
3653	06111	$1-2+3+4-56^*(7+8-(9A-B))$	$BA-987-(6-5)+4321$
3654	06112	$1-234^*5-(-6+78)^*-9^*A+B$	$-B+A-(9+876)-(-5-4321)$
3655	06113	$-1234+5678-9AB$	$BA-987+6-5+4321$
3656	06114	$12+3+4+56^*78+9-A-B$	$B+A9+87^*(-6+54)-(-3+2+1)$
3657	06115	$-1+2+3+4-5^*(6-789+A^*-B)$	$B+A-9+87^*65+4^*-321$
3658	06116	$-1-2^*3-45^*(-6-(7+89))-AB$	$B^*(A+987-654+3^*21)$
3659	06117	$-12-34^*(-56-78)+9^*(-A-B)$	$B+A98-7^*(65-43)^*-21$
365A	06118	$12+3+4-56^*-78-9-A+B$	$-BA+9+876^*5+4+32-1$
365B	06119	$-12-3+4-56^*-78-9-A+B$	$-B-A+(9+(-8+7+6))^5-4^*3)/2^*-1$
3660	06120	$-1-2^*-3^*(456+7)-(-8-9)^*AB$	$-B-A+9-876-(-5-4321)$
3661	06121	$-123+4+567-(-8+9AB)$	$-BA-9+8^*(7+6+5+4+3^*(2-1))$
3662	06122	$-1^*-2^*(-3^*(-4+5+6)+7)-(-8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A-9-(876-5)+4321$
3663	06123	$12+3+4-56^*-78+9+A+B$	$BA-(987-6)+5+4321$
3664	06124	$-123+4-56^*-78+9+A+B$	$B-A-9-876-(-5-4321)$
3665	06125	$-1-2^*-3-4^*(-5-6-(78+9AB))$	$-BA-9-(8+765)+4321$
3666	06126	$-1^*-2^*3^*(45-(-678+9A)+B)$	$B-A-9+876^*5-43-21$
3667	06127	$-12+3+4(4-56)^*(7-89+A-B)$	$-BA9-8-7+65^*43^*2+1$
3668	06128	$1+2^*3^*4^*5-6+7-8-9+A-B$	$-B-A^*98-(-7+65)+4321$
3669	06129	$1^*23^*(-4+5)^*(67+8+9AB)$	$B+A+9-8-7-6^*(5-4^*(3+2))^*1$
366A	06130	$-1-(-234-5-67^*8^*9)-A^*-B$	$-B+A+9-876-(-5-4321)$
366B	06131	$-1+2^*-3+4-56^*-78+9+A+B$	$B-A^*9-876^*-5+4^*(-3+2+1)$
3670	06132	$123-4-56^*-78-9A+B$	$B-A+9-876-5+4321$
3671	06133	$1-23^*4^*(-56+7)-8^*(9+A+B)$	$B+A+9-87^*-65+4^*-321$
3672	06134	$-1-(-2+3+4)-(-56^*78-9^*A-B)$	$B+A-9-876-5+4321$
3673	06135	$1-2+3+4+5^*6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A^*-98-76+5+4321$
3674	06136	$-1^*(-23-4+5)^*(-6+7)^*(89+AB)$	$-B-A9-(8+765-4321)$
3675	06137	$-123+4-(56-78^*-9^*-A+B)$	$-B-A9-8-76-5^*-43^*21$
3676	06138	$1-2-(-3^*-4-56^*78)-9^*-A-B$	$-B-A9-87+6+5^*43^*21$
3677	06139	$-1+2+3^*(4-56)^*(-7+89-AB)$	$-BA9-8+7-65^*-43^*2-1$
3678	06140	$-1+2-3+4-56^*-78-(-9A+B)$	$-BA9-8+7+65^*43^*-2^*-1$
3679	06141	$-1-23+4-5^*(-6-(7+89A)-B)$	$-BA-9-(-8+765-4321)$
367A	06142	$1+2-3+4-56^*-78+9A-B$	$BA+987+6^*5+43-21$
367B	06143	$1+2+3+4+5^*6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B-A9-876^*-5-43^*(-2+1)$
3680	06144	$1^*-2^*3^*(4+56-(7-(-89A-B)))$	$B+A-9-876+5+4321$
3681	06145	$1-2-3+4+5^*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-(-9-876^*5)-43+2^*-1$
3682	06146	$1^*2^*(-3+4+5-(-6^*-7^*-8^*9-A)-B)$	$B+A-9-(-876^*5+43+21)$
3683	06147	$12-3+(-45+67)^*(89+AB)$	$-BA+9^*8-76^*-54+321$
3684	06148	$1^*(-2-(-3+45))^*(6-7)^*(89-(A-B))$	$-B-A-(98+76)+5^*43^*21$
3685	06149	$-1+2^*3^*(-45+678-9+AB)$	$-B-(-A9+8)-(-7^*65+4+321)$
3686	06150	$-1^*2^*3^*(45-678-(-9+AB))$	$B-A-(9-876^*5)-43-2+1$
3687	06151	$1-2^*3^*(45-678-(-9+AB))$	$B+A+9^*8^*7+6^*5^*4^*3^*2+1$
3688	06152	$-1+2-3+4+56^*78-(-9-A^*B)$	$-B-A9-(-8+765-4321)$
3689	06153	$123+4+56^*7^*(-89-AB)$	$-B-A9+8-76-5^*43^*-21$
368A	06154	$-123+4+567-(8+9A)^*B$	$-B+A+98-(-7^*65+4+321)$
368B	06155	$1-2+3+4+5^*6-7+8+9+A-B$	$BA-(-987-6^*(5+43-2)^*1)$
3690	06156	$123^*(-4+5+6-(-7+89))^*(A-B)$	$-BA9+8+7-65^*-43^*-2^*-1$
3691	06157	$1-(23-4)-56^*-78+9A-B$	$-B+A9+8^*7^*-6-5^*-43^*21$
3692	06158	$-12+3+4+56^*-78+9A-B$	$B-(A9+8+765-4321)$
3693	06159	$-1+2^*-3+4^*(-5-6-7^*-8-(-9+AB))$	$-BA-(-9-8)-(-765-4321)$
3694	06160	$12^*(-3-(-456-(-78-(9A-B))))$	$-B^*-A^*(9+87+6-5+4+3-2+1)$
3695	06161	$-12-3+4^*(-6-7)-8-(-9+AB)$	$-BA-9^*8^*(7-6)-5^*43^*-21$
3696	06162	$-1-23-456-7^*8^*(9-AB)$	$B-(-A-9)-876-(-5-4321)$
3697	06163	$1-2-3+4+5^*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$-B-A-98-76^*(-5+4-3-2-1)$
3698	06164	$-1-23+4-56^*-78-9A^*-B$	$-B-A-9-876^*-5+4^*(-3-2+1)$
3699	06165	$12-3+4-56^*-78+9+A^*B$	$BA+987-6^*-5+4+3+2^*-1$
369A	06166	$1-(2+3+4)-(-5^*-678-9AB)$	$-B-A+9-876^*-5-4-3-2-1$
369B	06167	$1+2-3+4+5^*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9+(87+65)^*(-4+32+1)$
36A0	06168	$-12-3^*4+56^*78-9+AB$	$-B-A9+8-76^*5^*(-4-3)^*2^*1$
36A1	06169	$-1-(23+4+5^*6-7-8^*9A^*B)$	$B-A-(98+765)+4321$
36A2	06170	$1+23+4-56^*-78-9^*AB$	$-B+A98-7+6^*(5+4+3+2-1)$
36A3	06171	$1-2-3-4+56^*78-(-9A+B)$	$-BA-9+876^*5-4^*(-3-2-1)$
36A4	06172	$1^*2+3+4+5^*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA-9+8^*-7^*6+5^*43^*21$
36A5	06173	$-1-23-45^*(-6-7-(8+9+A+B))$	$BA9+8^*-7^*-65+4^*(32-1)$
36A6	06174	$-12^*-3^*(-4+5)^*(-6-7-8^*-9)^*(-A-B)$	$B-A9+8-(765-4321)$
36A7	06175	$-1-2+3+4^*(56-7^*-8)+9A^*B$	$-BA9+87^*65-(4+3+2+1)$
36A8	06176	$-12+3-4-56^*-78+9-A^*-B$	$B-(-A-(98-7^*65+4))-321$
36A9	06177	$-1-2^*-3+4^*56-78-9^*A^*-B$	$BA9+8^*7^*-6-5+4^*3^*-21$
36AA	06178	$-1+2+3^*4+5-6^*(-789+A^*B)$	$BA+9+8^*-7-65^*(-4+3^*-21)$
36AB	06179	$-12+3-4+56^*7^*-8^*(9-AB)$	$B-A+9+876^*5-(4+32-1)$
36B0	06180	$-12-3-4+56^*(-7-8)+9AB$	$BA+987-6^*(-5+43-2)+1$
36B1	06181	$12-3+4+5^*6+7+8+9AB$	$-B-A9^*-8^*(7-65+4+3+2+1)$
36B2	06182	$-1^*(-2+3+4+5+6+7+8-9-A)^*-B$	$-B^*(-A+9+876+65-432+1)$
36B3	06183	$-1^*23^*(4-(-5+6))-(-78+9+AB))$	$-B-(-A-9+876^*-5)+4-(32+1)$
36B4	06184	$1^*2^*3^*4+5+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-(-987-6)+5+4^*-3^*-21$
36B5	06185	$-1-23+4+56^*7^*-8-(-9-AB)$	$-BA9-(876+5^*4^*-321)$
36B6	06186	$12-3+4+56^*78+9+AB$	$B-(-A-9+876^*-5+4+3+2+1)$
36B7	06187	$1-23^*-4+5^*6+7+8-9A^*-B$	$-BA9-8+7^*65+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
36B8	06188	$12 - (3 - 4 + 56^* - 78) - (9^* - A - B)$	$B - (-A98 + 7 - 6^*543) + 2^*1$
36B9	06189	$1^*2 - 3 + 4 \wedge 5^*6 + 7^*8 - 9 + A - B$	$BA - (987 - 65 - 4321)$
36BA	06190	$-12 - 3^*(-456 - 7 + 8 - 9AB)$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 6^*(543 - 21)$
36BB	06191	$-1 - 2 - 345 - 6^* - 789 - (A - B)$	$BA - (9 - 876^*5 + 4^* - 32^* - 1)$
3700	06192	$1 - 2 - 345 - 6^*789^*(A - B)$	$BA - 9^* - 8^*(7 + 65) + 4 - 3 - (-2 + 1)$
3701	06193	$-1 + 2 - 345 - 6^* - 789 - (-A + B)$	$BA + 9 + 876 + 54^* - 3^* - 21$
3702	06194	$-1 + 2345 - (-678 - 9A^*B)$	$B - (A - 9 - 876^*5 - (-43 + 21))$
3703	06195	$-123 + 4 + 567^*8 - (9 + A + B)$	$B + A + 9^*(8^*7 + 6 + 5 \wedge 4 - 3 + 2) \wedge 1$
3704	06196	$1 + 2345 + 678 - 9A^* - B$	$B + A + 987 + 6^*(543 + 21)$
3705	06197	$-1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5^*678 + 9AB$	$-BA + 98 - 7^*(-654 - (-32 - 1))$
3706	06198	$1 - 2^*3 - 4 - 5^* - 678 + 9AB$	$-B - A^* - 9^*(-8 + 7 - (-65 - (-4 - 3))) - (2 - 1)$
3707	06199	$1 - (2 - 3 + 45^*67 - 8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA - 98 + 7^*654 - 32 - 1$
3708	06200	$-1 + 2 - (-345^*(6 + 7) + 89 - A + B)$	$-BA - (98 + 7^* - 654) + 32^* - 1$
3709	06201	$12 - 345 + 6^*(789 + A - B)$	$-BA - 98 + 7^*654 - (32 - 1)$
370A	06202	$12^*(345 - (-67 - 8 + 9A) - B)$	$-B + A^* - 98 - 7 - (-6 - 5) + 4321$
370B	06203	$-1 - 2 + 3 - 4 - 5^* - 678 + 9AB$	$-BA9 + 8 - 7^* - 65 + 4321$
3710	06204	$1^* - 2^* - 3^*(-4 + 5^*) * (6 - (7 - (89 - A)))^*B$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 65 - 4^*3 + 2^* - 1$
3711	06205	$1 - (234 - 567^*8) - (-9 - AB)$	$-B + A + 98 + 7 - 65^*(-4 - 3^*21)$
3712	06206	$-1 + 2 - (3 + 4 - 56^*78) - (-9 - AB)$	$-B + A^* - 98 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 4321$
3713	06207	$-1 + 2 + 3^*(-4 - (-567 - 89A)) + B$	$-BA - 98 - 76 - 5^* - 43^*21$
3714	06208	$1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \wedge 5^*6 + 7^*8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA - 9^*8^* - 76 + 5^*(-43 + 21)$
3715	06209	$12 - (3 - 4 - 56^*78 + 9 - AB)$	$-BA - 98 + 7^*65^*4^*3 - 2 + 1$
3716	06210	$1 + 2^*(-3 + 4) + 5^*678 + 9AB$	$B + A - 9 + 876^*5 - 4^*3^*(2 - 1)$
3717	06211	$-1 - 2 - 345 + 6^*789 + A + B$	$-BA + 98 - 7^*(-654 + 32 - 1)$
3718	06212	$1 \wedge 2 + 3 + 4 \wedge 5^*6 + 7^*8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 65 - (4 + 3 - 2) - 1$
3719	06213	$-1 - 23^*(4 - 567) - 89AB$	$-B - A - (-9 - 8 + 76^* - 54 - 321)$
371A	06214	$-1^*(234 + 5 - (6^*789 - AB))$	$BA + 9^* - 8^* - 7 + 654^* - 3^*2^* - 1$
371B	06215	$123 - 4567 - 89^* - AB$	$-BA9 - 87^*65^*(-4 + 3) - 2 - 1$
3720	06216	$-12 + 34 - 5^*(6 - 789 - AB)$	$B - A - 9 + 87^*(654 + 3 - 21)$
3721	06217	$-123 + 4 - (567^* - 8 + 9 + A - B)$	$B + A - 9 + 876^*5 - 4 - 3 + 2^*1$
3722	06218	$-1 - 2 - (34 + 56^* - 78 + 9^*(-A - B))$	$-BA9 + 87^*65 - (-4 + 3 + 2 - 1)$
3723	06219	$12 - 3 - 4 - 56^* - 78 - (-9 - AB)$	$B - A + 9 - 8 - (76^* - 54 - 321)$
3724	06220	$1 - 23 - 4 - 5^*(-6 - 789 - AB)$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 65^*(4 - 3) + 2^*1$
3725	06221	$-1 + 2 + 3456 - 7^* - 8^*9 + A^* - B$	$B - A^* - 9^*(87 - 6 + 5 + 4 - 32 + 1)$
3726	06222	$-1^*(-2 + 3^*) * (-4 - 5^* - (-67 + 8)) * (9 - AB)$	$-B - A - 9 + 876^*5 + 4 - 32^* - 1$
3727	06223	$-1 - 234 + 5 + 6^*789 - AB$	$-BA9 + 87^*65 + 4 + 3 + 2^* - 1$
3728	06224	$-1 + 2 + 3 + (4 - 5 + 6^*) * (789 + AB)$	$-B - A + 9 - 876^* - 5 + 43 - 21$
3729	06225	$-12 + 345 - 6^* - 7^*(8 + 9 + A + B)$	$B + A^*9^*(-8 + 7 + 6 + 54) + 3 + 2 - 1$
372A	06226	$-1^*(234 - 567 - 89 + A)^*B$	$B + A - (-987 - 6) - 54^* - 3^*21$
372B	06227	$-123 - 4 - 56^*(7 - (89 + A - B))$	$-B + A - 9^*(8 - 76 - (-5 + 432) - 1)$
3730	06228	$12 - (-3 - (4 - 5^* - 678 + 9AB))$	$-B - A9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5^* - 43^*21)$
3731	06229	$-123 - 4 - 567^* - 8 - 9 + A + B$	$-BA9 + 87^*65 + 4^*3 - 2 + 1$
3732	06230	$1 - 234 + 5 + 6^*(789 - A - B)$	$-BA9 + 87^*65 - 4^* - 3^*(2 - 1)$
3733	06231	$-1 - (23 + 4567) - 89A^* - B$	$-BA - 9 - 8 + 76^*(-5 - (-43 - 21))$
3734	06232	$-1^*234^*(-5 + 67 + 8 + 9 - A^*B)$	$-BA - 9 - 8^*(-7 + 6) - 5^*43^* - 21$
3735	06233	$1 - 23 - 4567 - 89A^* - B$	$BA9 - 87 - 6^* - 543 - 2 - 1$
3736	06234	$1^* - 2^*3^*(-4 - 567 - 89 - AB)$	$B + A - 9 + (8 - 7 + 6 \wedge 5^*4) / ((3 + 2)^*1)$
3737	06235	$-1 + 2 + 34 - (56^* - 78 + 9) + AB$	$-BA - 98 - 7^* - 654 + 3^*(-2 + 1)$
3738	06236	$1 + 2 + 3456 - (7^* - 8 + 9 + A)^*B$	$BA9 - 87 + 6^*543^*(2 - 1)$
3739	06237	$1 - 2^* - 3^*4 + 56^*78 - (-9 - AB)$	$-B^*(A9 - 8^* - 7 - 6 - (543 - 21))$
373A	06238	$-1 - 2 + 34 - 56^* - 78 + 9 + A + B$	$-BA + 98^*7 - 654^*3^*2^* - 1$
373B	06239	$1 + 23 + 4 - 5^* - 678 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 87 + 6^*543 + 2 + 1$
3740	06240	$1^*(2 - 3 + 45)^*(6 - (7 - (-8 + 9A) - B))$	$-B - A9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^* - 43^* - 21$
3741	06241	$1 - 23 - 45 + 67^* - 8^*(-9 + A - B)$	$B - A - (9 - (-87 - 654))^* - 3^* - 2^* - 1$
3742	06242	$-1234 + 5678 - 9A^*B$	$-B + A9^* - 8 - 7 - (65 - 4321)$
3743	06243	$-1234 - (-5 + 67^* - 89 - A + B)$	$BA - 98 - 76^* - 54 + 321$
3744	06244	$-1 - (234 - 5) - (-6^*789 - A^* - B)$	$-BA - 9^*8 - 7^* - 654 - 32^*1$
3745	06245	$123 - 4 - 5^* - 678 - 9A^* - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8^* - 7^* - 6^*(-5^*4 + 3/2) - 1$
3746	06246	$-1234 + 5 + 6 + 78^*9 + A + B$	$-B - A - 9 - 8 - (765 - 4321)$
3747	06247	$-1 + 234 - 5^*(-6 - 7 + 8 + 9^* - AB)$	$B + A + (-9 + (-8 + 7 + 6)^*5 \wedge 4 - 3)^*2 \wedge 1$
3748	06248	$1 - 23 - (-4 + 567^* - 8 - 9 + AB)$	$-B^*(-A9 - (8 - 76 + 54) - 321)$
3749	06249	$1 - 2^*3 + (-567 + 8)^*(-9 - (A - B))$	$-BA + 9 - (-8 + 7) + 6 + 5^* - 43^* - 21$
374A	06250	$1 - 23 + 4567 - 8 - 9AB$	$-B - (-A9 + 876 - 5) + 4321$
374B	06251	$1 - 2 - 3^*(-4 - (567 - (-89A - B)))$	$B + A + 9 + (8 - 7 + 6 \wedge 5^*4) / ((3 + 2)^*1)$
3750	06252	$12 + 3^* - 4 - 5^*(-6 - (789 + AB))$	$-B - (A - 9) + 8^*(7 + 6 - (543 + 2 - 1))$
3751	06253	$12 + 3 + 4^* - 567 - 8^* - 9^*AB$	$B - A + 9 + 876^*5 - 4 + 32 - 1$
3752	06254	$(-1 + 2 \wedge 3 + 4 \wedge 5 - 6^*7^*8)^*9 + A - B$	$-B - A - (-9 + 87 - (-6 + 5^*43^*21))$
3753	06255	$1 - (-2 - (34 + 56^*78) - 9) + AB$	$B - (A - 9) - (-8 + 76^* - 54 - 321)$
3754	06256	$-12 + 3 + 4 + 567^*8 - 9A - B$	$-B - A9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5^*43^* - 21$
3755	06257	$-1 - (-2 + 3 + 4567 - 89A^*B)$	$B + A - 9 - 876^* - 5 - 4 + 32 + 1$
3756	06258	$-1^*(-2 + 3 + 4567 - 89A^*B)$	$-BA - 98 - (765 - 4321)$
3757	06259	$-123 + 4567 - 89A - B$	$-B - (A + 9 - 876^*5 - 4) + 3^*21$
3758	06260	$1^*(-2 + 3 - 456 + 7 + 8)^*(-9 + A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 876^*7 + 6^*(5 + 4 \wedge (3 + 2)) \wedge 1$
3759	06261	$12 + 34 + 5^*678 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 87 - 6^* - 543 + 21$
375A	06262	$-1 + 23 + 4^* - 567 + 8^*9^*AB$	$B + A9 - 876 - 5 + 4321$
375B	06263	$1 - 2 - 3 + 4 - 567^* - 8 - 9A - B$	$B - A + 9 + 876^*5 - (-4 - 32 - 1)$
3760	06264	$-1 - (23 - 4567 - 8 + 9AB)$	$-B - A + 9 - 8 - 765 + 4321$
3761	06265	$-12 - (-3 - 4567 + 8 + 9AB)$	$BA - 9 - 876 + 5 + 4321$
3762	06266	$1 - 23 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$-BA - (98 - 7^*654 - 3 - 21)$
3763	06267	$-1 - 23^*(-45 - 67 - 89) - AB$	$BA - 9 - 876^* - 5 - (43 + 21)$
3764	06268	$-1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 567^*8 + 9 - AB$	$B - A - 9 - 8 - 765 + 4321$
3765	06269	$-1234 + 56 - 78^*9^* - A - B$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 6 - (5 - 4321)$
3766	06270	$12 - 3 - 4567 + 89A^*B$	$B + A - 9 + 876^*5 + 43 - 2 - 1$
3767	06271	$1^*234 - 56^* - 78 - 9A - B$	$BA + 9^* - 8^* - 76 - (5 + 4)^*(32 + 1)$
3768	06272	$1 - 234 + 56^*(-7 + 89) + AB$	$B - (-A9 + 876 - 5) + 4321$
3769	06273	$1 + 2^*(3 - 4) + 5^*(-6 - 7 + 89A) - B$	$BA + 9 - 876 - 5 + 4321$
376A	06274	$-1 - 2 - (-3 - 4 - 567^*8 - 9) - AB$	$B - (A98 + 76^* - 5) + 4321$
376B	06275	$-12 - 3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 + 6^* - 5^*4^* - 32 + 1$
3770	06276	$-1 - 2 + 3 + 4567 - 8 - 9AB$	$BA - 9 + 8^*(-7 + 6)^* - 543 - 21$
3771	06277	$-1 - 2 - 34^*(-56 - 7 - 89 + A + B)$	$B + A98^*7 - 6^* - 543^*(-2 + 1)$
3772	06278	$-12 + 34 - 567^* - 8 - 9 - AB$	$B - (A + 9 - 876^*5 - (43 + 21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3773	06279	$1 - (-234 + 56^* - 78 - (9 - AB))$	$-B - A^*(98 - 7) - (-6 - (5 + 4321))$
3774	06280	$-1 + 2 + 345^*(6 + 7) + 89 - AB$	$-B - (A - 9) - (-8 + 765 - 4321)$
3775	06281	$-123 + 4567 - (89A - B)$	$B - A - 98^*7^* - 6 - 54^*(3 - 21)$
3776	06282	$1 + 2 + 3 + 4567 - 8 - 9AB$	$-B + A - (9 - 8) - (765 - 4321)$
3777	06283	$-1 - 234 + 5 - 6^*(-789 + A) - B$	$BA + 9 - 876 - (-5 - 4321)$
3778	06284	$1 - (2 - (-34 + 5)) + 67^* - 8^*(-9 + A - B)$	$B - A - 9 + 8 - 765 + 4321$
3779	06285	$-1 + 23 - 4567 - 89A^* - B$	$BA - 9 + 8^*(7 - 6 + 543 - 2 - 1)$
377A	06286	$1^*23 - 4567 - 89A^* - B$	$B - A + 9 - (8 + 765) + 4321$
377B	06287	$-12 + 3^*4^*5^*(-6 + 7)^*89 - (A - B)$	$B - A9 - 8^*76^*(-5 - 4) - 3^*21$
3780	06288	$1 - 2 - 3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - (765 - 4321)$
3781	06289	$-1 - 2^*(3 + 4^* - 5^*)^*(67 + 89 - A + B)$	$BA - 9 + 876^*5 - 43 - 2 - 1$
3782	06290	$-1 + 2 - (3 - 4567) + 8 - 9AB$	$-B + A9^* - 8^* - 7 - 654 + 3^*2 - 1$
3783	06291	$1 + 2 + (-3 - 45 + 6 - (7 - 89))^*AB$	$B + A + (-9 + 8/7)^*6^*(-5 - 4 \cdot 3^*2)^{\wedge}1$
3784	06292	$-1 - 2 + 3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$B^*(A - 9 + 8 - 7^* - 65 - 4 + 3 + 21)$
3785	06293	$12 - 3^*4 + 567^*8 + 9 + A^* - B$	$BA - (9 + 876^* - 5 + 43) - (-2 + 1)$
3786	06294	$1 - (2 - 3 - 4567 - 8 + 9AB)$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 65 + 43 + 21$
3787	06295	$-1 - (2 - 3 - (4 - 567^* - 8)) - 9^*A - B$	$BA - 9 + 876^*5 - 43 + 2 + 1$
3788	06296	$-1 + 2 - (3 - 4567 - (8 - 9AB))$	$-B + A9 + 876^*5 - 4 - 3 - 21$
3789	06297	$-1 - 23 + 4567 + (8 + 9A)^* - B$	$BA - (-98 - 7^*654 + 321)$
378A	06298	$12 + 3^* - 4 - 5^*(6 - (-7 + 89A)) + B$	$-BA9 - 876 + 5432 - 1$
378B	06299	$1 + 2^*3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$-BA + 9^* - 8^* - 76 - 5 + 4 + 32^* - 1$
3790	06300	$-1 - 2^*34^* - 56 + (-78 - 9)^* - A + B$	$-BA9 - (876 - 5432 - 1)$
3791	06301	$1 - (-2 - 3) - (-4 - 567^*8) - 9^*A - B$	$-B + A9 + 87^*6 - 5 - 4^*(-32 + 1)$
3792	06302	$-1^*2^*(3 + 45 - 67)^*(8 + 9A + B)$	$B - (A - 9) - (-8 - (-765 + 4321))$
3793	06303	$12 - 3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$B - (A98 + 7 - 65^* - 43^* - 2) + 1$
3794	06304	$1 + 23 + 4567 - 8 - 9AB$	$B + A - (9 - 8 - (-765 + 4321))$
3795	06305	$-1 + 2 + 345 + 67^*8^*9 + AB$	$B - A + 9 - 87 - (-6 + 5^*4)^* - 321$
3796	06306	$1 - (2 + 3456) - (-789 + A)^*B$	$B - A9^* - 8^*7 - (654 + 3 - 2^*1)$
3797	06307	$1 + 2 + 345 + 67^*8^*9 + AB$	$-BA + 98 + 7^* - 6 + 5^* - 43^* - 21$
3798	06308	$-1 - 23 + 4^*(-56 + 78 + 9A)^*B$	$BA9 - 8^*7 + 6^*543 + 21$
3799	06309	$12 + 3 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$-BA - 9 - 8 - 7^* - 654 - 3 - 21$
379A	06310	$-12 - 345 + 6^*789 + AB$	$BA - 98 - 765 + 4321$
379B	06311	$12 - 34 - 56^*(7 - 89) - AB$	$BA - 9 - 876^* - 5 - (4 + 3 + 21)$
37A0	06312	$-1 - 23 + 4^*(56 - (-78 - 9AB))$	$BA - (-9 + 876^* - 5 + 43 + 2^* - 1)$
37A1	06313	$1 - (2 - 3) - (-4^* - 5 + 6^*(-7 + 89^* - A)) - B$	$-BA + 9 - 8 - 7^*(-654 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
37A2	06314	$-12^*(34 + 567 + 8 - 9A^*B)$	$B^*(-A - 98 + 76 - 5 + 432 + 1)$
37A3	06315	$12 - (-34 - 56^*78) - 9^*(-A - B)$	$-BA - 9 - 8 + 7^*654 + 3 - 21$
37A4	06316	$-12 - 3 - 4 - 56^*(7 - 89) - AB$	$-BA - (-9 + 8 + 7^* - 654 - (-32 - 1))$
37A5	06317	$1 - (-2 + 3 - (4 + 567^*8)) - (9^*A - B)$	$BA + 987 + 6^*(543 + 21)$
37A6	06318	$-1 + 23 + 4567 - (-8 + 9AB)$	$B - (-A9 - 87 + (65 + 4)^*3^* - 21)$
37A7	06319	$1^*23 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$BA + 9 + 876^*5 - 4 - 32^*1$
37A8	06320	$1 + 23 + 4567 + 8 - 9AB$	$-BA9 - 87^* - 65 + 43^*2^*1$
37A9	06321	$-1 - 2 - 345 + 6^*789 + AB$	$-BA - 9 + 87 - 6 - 5^*43^* - 21$
37AA	06322	$1 - (-2 + 345 + 6^*(-789 - A - B))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 765 + 4321$
37AB	06323	$-1 + 2345 + 678 + 9AB$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 - (-6^*543 + 2 - 1)$
37B0	06324	$-1^*(-2345 - (678 + 9AB))$	$-B + A9 + 876^*5 - 4 - 3 + 2 + 1$
37B1	06325	$1 - (-2345 - 678 - 9AB)$	$-B^*(A + 9 - (8 + 7)^*(-6 + 5 + 4) + 3)^*21$
37B2	06326	$-1 + 2 - (-34 - 567^*8 + 9A - B)$	$B + A9 + 87 + 65^*(4 - 3^* - 21)$
37B3	06327	$-123^*(4 - 5 + 67 - 8 - 9A + B)$	$-B + A9 - (8 - 76^*54 - 321)$
37B4	06328	$1^* - 2 - (-3456 + 7^* - 8^* - 9^*(A - B))$	$-BA - (-9 + 8) + 7^* - 65^*4^* - 3 - (-2 + 1)$
37B5	06329	$-12 + 3 + 4^*(56 + 78 + 9AB)$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 - 6^* - 543 - 21$
37B6	06330	$1 - 2 + 34 - 567^* - 8 - 9^*A - B$	$-BA9 + 87^*65 - 4^*(-3 - 21)$
37B7	06331	$1234 + 5^*(678 + 9 - A^*B)$	$-BA - 9 - 8 + 7^*654 - 3 - (2 + 1)$
37B8	06332	$-123 + 4 - 567^* - 8 + 9A - B$	$-BA - (-9 - 8 - 7^*654 + 32 + 1)$
37B9	06333	$12 - 345 + 6^*(789 + A + B)$	$-BA + 9^* - 8^* - 76 + 5 - 4 - 3^*2^*1$
37BA	06334	$-1 - 2 - 3 - 4^*(-56 - 78 - 9AB)$	$B - A - (-98 - 76^*54 - 321)$
37BB	06335	$-12 + 3^* - 4 - (-5^*(6 - 7)^* - 89A - B)$	$-B - A + 9^*8 - 765 + 4321$
3800	06336	$12 - 34 - (567^* - 8 + 9) - A - B$	$-B^*(-A9 + 8 + 7 - (6 - 5 + 4 + 321))$
3801	06337	$-1 + 234 - 5^*(67 - 89A - B)$	$BA + 9 + 876^*5 - 4^* - 3^* - 2^*1$
3802	06338	$1 + 23 - 45^* - 6 - 7^*8^*(-9A + B)$	$-BA - 98^*7 - 65 + 4321$
3803	06339	$1 + (-2^* - 3)^{\wedge}4^*5 - (6 - (-7 - 8)^*9) + A - B$	$B - A9 - 8 + 76 + 5^* - 43^* - 21$
3804	06340	$-123 - 4 - 5^*(-6 - 7 + 8 + 9A^* - B)$	$-BA + 9 + 876 - 76 - 5^* - 43^*21$
3805	06341	$((1 + 2)^{\wedge}3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6)^*(7 + 8 - 9) + A - B$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 - 6^*(-543 + 2) - 1$
3806	06342	$-12^*(-345 - (67 + 8 - 9 - A^*B))$	$-B + A98 - 765^* - 4 + 321$
3807	06343	$1 - 2^*(-3^*4^{\wedge}5 + (-6 - 7)^*8) - 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 7^* - 654 - 3 - 21$
3808	06344	$-123 + 4 - (-567^*8 - 9) + A^*B$	$-B - (A9 - 87 - 6) + 5^* - 43^* - 21$
3809	06345	$1 - 234 - 5 + 6^*789 - (-A + B)$	$-B + A98 - (7 - 6)^* - 54^* - 3^* - 21$
380A	06346	$1^*2 + 3^*(4 + 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7 + 8^* - 9 + A - B$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7^*(-654 - (-3 + 2))^* - 1$
380B	06347	$-1^*(-23 - 456 + 78)^*(9 - A)^* - B$	$BA + 987 + 6 - 54^*3^* - 21$
3810	06348	$-12 - 34 + 567^*8 + 9 - A + B$	$-BA - 98 - (7 - 6 + 5^* - 43^*21)$
3811	06349	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 5^*6^*7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$BA9 - 8 - 7 - (-6^*543 - 21)$
3812	06350	$-1 - 23 - 4 - 567^* - 8 - (9 - A) - B$	$-BA - (-98 - (7 - 6)) - 5^*43^* - 21$
3813	06351	$1234 - 5 - 6^*7^* - 89 - A^*B$	$-B + A - 98 + 7^*654 - 3 - 21$
3814	06352	$1 - 2 - 345 + 6 + 7^* - 8^*(9 - AB)$	$-B - (A9 + 8) - (7^* - 654 - 3) + 2 - 1$
3815	06353	$-123 + 4567 - 8 + 9^* - AB$	$-BA9 - 8^* - 765 + 432^* - 1$
3816	06354	$1 - (-2 - 3456 + 7^* - 8^*9) - (-A - B)$	$-B - (-A9 - 876^*5) + 4 - (3 - 21)$
3817	06355	$12 - 34 - (-567^*8 - (-9 + A)^* - B)$	$-B + A - 9^* - 8 - 765 + 4321$
3818	06356	$-1^*2^*(-3 - 4^* - 567^*(8 - 9) + A + B)$	$B - (-A + 9^*87^* - 6 - 543) + 2^*1$
3819	06357	$-123 - 4 - 567^* - 8 - (-9 - AB)$	$-B + A - 9^*87^* - 6 + 543 + 21$
381A	06358	$(-1 + (-2^{\wedge}3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6)^*7^*8)/9 + A - B$	$B^*(A - 98 - 76 + 543 + 2 + 1)$
381B	06359	$-1 - 23 + 4 - 567^* - 8 - 9^*(-A + B)$	$B - A - (98 - 7^*654) - (-3 + 21)$
3820	06360	$1^*2^*3^*4^*(56 - (-78 - (9A - B)))$	$-B + A9 - (876^*5 - 4 - (3 + 21))$
3821	06361	$-1234 + 5678 + 9^* - AB$	$-B - A9 + 8 - 7^* - 654 + 3^*(-2 + 1)$
3822	06362	$1 - 2^*(-3^*(4^{\wedge}5 + 6^*7) + 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B - A9 + (-87 - 65)^*4^* - 3^*(-2 + 1)$
3823	06363	$1 - 234 - 5^*(-67 - 89A + B)$	$BA98 + 7 - 6^* - 54^*(-32 + 1)$
3824	06364	$1^*(2 + 34 - 5)^*(67 - 8 + 9^*A + B)$	$B - (-A98 - 765^*4 - 321)$
3825	06365	$-12 - (-3 + 4) - (-567^*8 - 9 + A + B)$	$BA9 + 8 - (7 + 6^* - 543) + 21$
3826	06366	$123 + 4 + 56^*78 + 9 + A^*B$	$B - A9 + 87 + 6 + 5^*43^*21$
3827	06367	$-123 - 45 - (6 + 7^*8^* - 9A) - B$	$-B + A9 + 8 - 7^*(-654 + 3) + 2^*1$
3828	06368	$123 - (4 + 56^* - 78 - 9A) + B$	$B + A + 9^*8 + (7/((6 + 5)^{\wedge}4^*3 + 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
3829	06369	$-1 + 2 + 34^* - 5^* - 67 + 8^* - 9^*AB$	$BA + 9 - 876^* - 5 - (-4 - (3 + 2 - 1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
382A	06370	$-12*(3+4+5*(-67+8))-(9A-B)$	$-B-A9+876*5+4*3*21$
382B	06371	$-1-234+5*(-67-(8-9AB))$	$-B+A9-(876*5-4-32-1)$
3830	06372	$1*-23*-4*(5+6-(78-(9+AB)))$	$B-A98-(7+6)*(5-432*1)$
3831	06373	$-12-(-3-4)+56-7*(8-9*A)*B$	$-BA-(-9-8-(7*654+3-2+1))$
3832	06374	$123-4+5*678+9AB$	$-BA+9+8+7*654+3*(2-1)$
3833	06375	$-12+345*(6+7)-(-89+A+B)$	$BA-9-876*-5+4+3+21$
3834	06376	$1-2+345-6*(-789+AB)$	$B-A-(98+7*-654+3*2)+1$
3835	06377	$-1-2+34-5*(6-(7+89A)-B)$	$-BA-9*87+65+4321$
3836	06378	$-123-4-56-7*8*-9A+B$	$-B-(-A-9*-8*-76)-(54+32-1)$
3837	06379	$123-4-56*-78+9+AB$	$-B-A+98-765+4321$
3838	06380	$1*2*(-3-4*-567+8+(-9+A))*-B$	$B*-A*(-98-(7-6-(54-3*2+1)))$
3839	06381	$1-2-34-567*-8+9+A+B$	$-B+A+987-(-6-5)*(-4+321)$
383A	06382	$123+4-5*-678+9AB$	$B-A-98-(-7*654*(3-2)-1)$
383B	06383	$-12-3-(4-567*8+9-A-B)$	$BA9-8*-7-6*(-543+2)*1$
3840	06384	$1*2*-3*(4-5-678-9A+B)$	$B+A9+876*5-4+32*1$
3841	06385	$-123+4-(-5+6*-789)-AB$	$BA-9+876*5+4+32*1$
3842	06386	$-12+34*-5*(67+8-(9-A*-B))$	$B-(-A+9*87)-65+4321$
3843	06387	$12+3-(4+56)*(7-89+A+B)$	$-BA-9*-8-7*-654-32-1$
3844	06388	$-123-4-(5+6*-789)+A*-B$	$BA-98-7-(6-5*43*21)$
3845	06389	$1+2*-34*5+6*789-A*-B$	$BA9+8*7-6*(-543+2-1)$
3846	06390	$-1+234-56*-78-9*(-A+B)$	$-BA*(-9+8)*(-7-6+5+43+2)*1$
3847	06391	$1+234*56-(7+89AB)$	$B*(A-(-9-87+6*-54-3*21))$
3848	06392	$1+234+56*78+9*(A-B)$	$B-(-A9+876*-5)-(-4-32*1)$
3849	06393	$-1+2*-34*-56+789-(A-B)$	$-BA-(-9-8)-(-7*654+3)+21$
384A	06394	$-1+234-5-6*-78*(9-A)*-B$	$-B+A9-8-765+4321$
384B	06395	$-1*(2+3+4+567*-8-(-9+A+B))$	$-BA+98-7*-654-3*21$
3850	06396	$-1*(2-(345-6)-7*8)*(-9+A+B)$	$-BA+9*8*76+5*4+32*1$
3851	06397	$-1-2+(-3+4)*-567*-8+9+A-B$	$B-A9-(-87-6)*-5*4*-3-21$
3852	06398	$1*-2-345*6*-7+89A*-B$	$B-A9-8+7*654-(-3-21)$
3853	06399	$-1-2-(3-4567)-(-8-9A*-B)$	$-B+A-(-98+765)+4321$
3854	06400	$-1-2345-6*7+8*9A*B$	$B-A-9*(-8*(-76-5)-43+2)*-1$
3855	06401	$1+2-3-4-5*(-6+7)*(-89A-B)$	$B-A+98-765+4321$
3856	06402	$-1-23+4567-89A-B$	$-B*(A+98-(76+5+432)+1)$
3857	06403	$-1*(23-4567+89A+B)$	$B+A+987-(6+5)*(4-321)$
3858	06404	$1-23-(-4567+89A+B)$	$BA9-87-6-54*-3*21$
3859	06405	$-1+234+5*678+9A*B$	$-B+A98-76*(5+4)*-3*-2*-1$
385A	06406	$1234-5*(67+8)*(-9-(-A+B))$	$B-A9-(8-7)-(-6+5*43)*21$
385B	06407	$12+3+(-4+567)*8+9+A+B$	$B+A-(-98+7*-654+3*2*-1)$
3860	06408	$1+23-(4-567*8+9+A-B)$	$B+A+9+((-8+7+6)^5+4^3)*2^1$
3861	06409	$-1+2+3+4567-8+9A*-B$	$BA-9-8-765+4321$
3862	06410	$-1*(-2+3+4)*(-5-6-78-9*AB)$	$-B-(-A9-(8-765)-4321)$
3863	06411	$12-3-4-5*(-6-(7+89A))-B$	$B+A98-7*(-65-432-1)$
3864	06412	$12+34-56*(7-89)+A*-B$	$-BA+9*(8+7)*6-5+4321$
3865	06413	$12+3-4+567*8+9+A-B$	$-B*(-A+9)*(-87*-6-5*(-4-3))*(-2+1)$
3866	06414	$-1-2*-34*5*-6-7*(-89A+B)$	$BA-9*-8*-7-65*-4*(-3+21)$
3867	06415	$-1+2+345*(6+7)-(-8+9)+A*B$	$-B-A*987+654*(-3+21)$
3868	06416	$12-3+4-567*-8+9*(-A+B)$	$B+A9-8-765+4321$
3869	06417	$-1-2-3+4567+8+9A*-B$	$BA9+8*7*(6-5-4)*(-3-21)$
386A	06418	$-12-3*-4+5*6*(78-9+AB)$	$B-A9*8-(7-65-4321)$
386B	06419	$-12+3+4567-89A-B$	$B-A9*-8+7*6*54*(-3+2-1)$
3870	06420	$-123+4567+8*(-9-AB)$	$BA-(-9+8*(-7-6-543)+2+1)$
3871	06421	$1+2-(3-4567-8)-9A*B$	$B+A+98-765+4321$
3872	06422	$12+3-(-4567+8+9A*B)$	$-B-(A-9*-87)-(-6+5-4321)$
3873	06423	$-1-2*3+4567-89A-B$	$B+A-98+7*654-3+21$
3874	06424	$-1-23+4567-89A+B$	$B*(A-9+8*7+6-(-54-321))$
3875	06425	$-1-(-2-3)-(-4567-8)-9A*B$	$BA-9+8-765+4321$
3876	06426	$1-23-(-4567+89A)+B$	$B+A9+876*5+43+21$
3877	06427	$-1-2+3456-7*-89-AB$	$BA+9-8-765+4321$
3878	06428	$-1+2-(3-4567)-(-89A+B)$	$-BA-9-(-8-7*654)-3*-21$
3879	06429	$-1-2345-6-7+8*-9A*-B$	$BA-9+8*(7-(-6-543-2-1))$
387A	06430	$-1-(-23-(4+567*8)-(-9+A-B))$	$-BA-9*-8*76+54-(-3-21)$
387B	06431	$12+3+4-5*(6-7-89A-B)$	$BA9-(-8-(-76+54*-3*-21))$
3880	06432	$1*2*(3-456-7-(89A+B))$	$B+A9+8-(765-4321)$
3881	06433	$1+2+3456-(7*-89+AB)$	$B-A9*8+76-(5-4321)$
3882	06434	$-1+2+3+4567-89A-B$	$-B-A-987-65*-43*-2*-1$
3883	06435	$-12-3+4567-89A+B$	$B*(-A9+8-76+543+21)$
3884	06436	$1+2-(-3-4567-(-89A-B))$	$B+A*-9*-8*7+654+321$
3885	06437	$12-3+4-(567*-8-9-A-B)$	$B+A98-(76+5)*-43+21$
3886	06438	$-1*-2*(-3+4*567-89+AB)$	$B-(-A9+876*-5+4*(3-21))$
3887	06439	$1-2+34-(-567*8-9)+A-B$	$-BA+98+76-5*-43*21$
3888	06440	$12*(345+67-89-A+B)$	$-BA+9*-8*-76+54+32*1$
3889	06441	$12-3+4567-(89A+B)$	$-B+A+9*-87+(-6+5)*-4321$
388A	06442	$1*-2*(-3-4*(567+8)-(-9+A)+B)$	$-B+A-9*87-(-6+5-4321)$
388B	06443	$-123-4+5-6+7*-8*-9A+B$	$B+A+98-765+4321$
3890	06444	$-1+2-(-34-567*8*(-9+A))+B$	$BA9+87-6*-543-2*-1$
3891	06445	$123+4-567*-8+9-AB$	$-B+A+9-8*-7+6+5*-43*-21$
3892	06446	$-1-2-3+4567-89A+B$	$-B*(A-9+87-65-432+1)$
3893	06447	$123+4567-8-9AB$	$BA-98+7*654-3*21$
3894	06448	$-123-45-6*(-789-A+B)$	$-BA+98+7*654-(-3+21)$
3895	06449	$1+23+4567+8-9A*B$	$B+A-9*((-8-7)*6-5^4)-3*2-1$
3896	06450	$-1+2-3+4567-89A+B$	$B+A+(9+8)*7+(6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$
3897	06451	$-1+2-(-3-4*-5)+67*(-8-9*-A)-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*-7*-6*(-5-4)+3+2-1$
3898	06452	$-1-2+3+4567-89A+B$	$-B-A+9*-8*-76*(5-4)+3*-2-1$
3899	06453	$-12+3-4+56*(7+89)*(-A+B)$	$-B+A-987+65*43*2-1$
389A	06454	$1-2+3-(-4567+89A)+B$	$-B-A+9+8+7*654+32*-1$
389B	06455	$-123-45-6*-789-(A-B)$	$-B+A-9*-8+(-7-65)*(-43-21)$
38A0	06456	$-1+2+3+4567-89A+B$	$BA9+87+654*(3+2)*1$
38A1	06457	$1*23+4567-89A-B$	$B-A-987+65*-43*-2+1$
38A2	06458	$1+23+4567-89A-B$	$-B-(A-9*8*76)-(-5-4-(-3+2+1))$
38A3	06459	$(-1+(-2*3)^4)*5+6/(7-8)-9+A-B$	$B-A-9+8-7*-654-32+1$
38A4	06460	$-12-(34+567*-8+9)+AB$	$BA9+87-6*(-543-(2+1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
38A5	06461	$(1+2+3)^4 \cdot 5+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A9^*(87-65-4+3+21)$
38A6	06462	$1234-5+6^7 \cdot 89-A+B$	$-B-A-9-(-87+6-5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21)$
38A7	06463	$123+4567+8-9AB$	$-B-A-9-8-7^*-654+3+2^*1$
38A8	06464	$-1-23+45^*(6+78)+9A^*B$	$-B-A^*(-9+8)+76-5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
38A9	06465	$12+3456-(7^*-89+A^*B)$	$BA-9^*-8^*76-5+4^*-32^*1$
38AA	06466	$-1-(23+45)+6^*789-AB$	$B+A+9^*(8+7+(6+5-4)^3)^2+1$
38AB	06467	$-12-34+567^*8-(-9A-B)$	$B-A9-8-7^*-6^*(5-4^*-32)-1$
38B0	06468	$12^*(3-(4-5+6-(7+8+9)))^*(A+B)$	$-B^*(-A+9)^*(-87+65+432)^*1$
38B1	06469	$12+3-(-4567+89A)+B$	$-BA+98+7^*654-(-3+2)^*-1$
38B2	06470	$-1-2^*-34^*(56+7+8)-9^*(-A+B)$	$-B-A+9-(-8-7^*654-(3-21))$
38B3	06471	$12+34^*-5-6^*-789-A-B$	$-BA+98+7^*654+3+2^*1$
38B4	06472	$(1+2+3)^4 \cdot 5+6+(7-8)^9+A-B$	$B+A-9-(8-7^*(654-(3+2)+1))$
38B5	06473	$1-(-2-3^*-45)-6^*(-789+A)+B$	$-B+A-9^*(-87-65)^4 \cdot 3-2-1$
38B6	06474	$1^*(-23-(4-5))^*(-6-7-89-AB)$	$-B-A+9-8+7^*654-3+2-1$
38B7	06475	$12+3456-7^*-8^*9+AB$	$BA-(-98+76^*-54)+321$
38B8	06476	$1^*-234-5+6^*789+AB$	$B+A-98+7^*654-3^*-21$
38B9	06477	$12-3-4-5^*(-6-7-89A-B)$	$B-(A-9-8)+7^*654-32+1$
38BA	06478	$-1-(-23-4567+89A)+B$	$BA+9^*-8^*(7+6-54-32+1)$
38BB	06479	$-1^*(-23-4567+89A-B)$	$-B+A9-(876^*-5+4^*-32+1)$
3900	06480	$-12-3+4+567^*8-9-A^*-B$	$B+A-(-9^*8^*76-5)-(-43-21)$
3901	06481	$12+3-4-56^*(-7+89)^*(A-B)$	$B-A-9^*-8^*76+5^*-4^*(3-(2+1))$
3902	06482	$1+2^*3^*(4+5)/6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A9+8-7^*(-6-543^*(2-1))$
3903	06483	$-1+2-(-3-(-456-7)^*(8-9)^*A+B)$	$BA-98-(7^*654+32)-1$
3904	06484	$-12+3-4+567^*8+9A-B$	$-B-(A-9)+8-(7^*654+3+21)$
3905	06485	$-1-234+5-(-6^*789-AB)$	$BA-98+7^*654-32+1$
3906	06486	$123+4-5^*6^*(-78-9A)+B$	$-B-A-(9-(-8+7^*654))+3+21$
3907	06487	$1-(234-5)+6^*789+AB$	$BA-9-8-(7+6-5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21)$
3908	06488	$-12-(34+5+6^*-789)-AB$	$B-A^*9^*-87-(-654-3)^*(-2-1)$
3909	06489	$-1+2-3+4-5-6^*(-78-9^*A^*B)$	$-B-A^*(98-7^*-6+5^*-4^*(3-2+1))$
390A	06490	$-1-23+4-567^*-8-9+AB$	$B^*A^*(9-87-(-65-43-21))$
390B	06491	$-1-2^*34^*(-56-7-8)-(9-A-B)$	$-B-(A-98)-(-7+6+5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21)$
3910	06492	$-12+3+4+567^*8+9A-B$	$B-(A-9)-8-(7^*654+3)-2-1$
3911	06493	$1-(-234-5^*(6+7))^*(89-A)+B$	$-BA-9-8^*76-5+4321$
3912	06494	$12+3456-(7^*(-89+A)+B)$	$-B+A-9-(-8+7^*-654+3)+2+1$
3913	06495	$12-34+567^*8-(-9A-B)$	$BA+98+7^*(654-32+1)$
3914	06496	$-1^*2^*(3-4+5^*6)^*-7^*(8+9-(-A+B))$	$BA9+87+6^*5^*4^*(32+1)$
3915	06497	$1-(2-3)-4-567^*-8-(-9A+B)$	$-BA-98+7^*(654+32-1)$
3916	06498	$1+2-34-5^*(6-7-8-9A^*B)$	$-B-A+9+8+7^*654+3-(-2-1)$
3917	06499	$1-23+4+567^*8+9A+B$	$BA-9^*-8-76-5^*-43^*21$
3918	06500	$-123+4-56^*(-78-9)-(-A-B)$	$-B+A9-(-8+7-6)+5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
3919	06501	$1+2+3^*-45+6^*789-(A+B)$	$B+A+98^*-7-65+4321$
391A	06502	$1+2^*-3+(-456+7)^*-8+9AB$	$B-A-9-8-7^*-654-3+21$
391B	06503	$-1+2+3456-7^*(-89+A)+B$	$B+A9+876^*5+43^*(2+1)$
3920	06504	$-12+3^*-45+6^*789+A-B$	$-BA-98+7^*(654-32^*-1)$
3921	06505	$12-(3+45)-6^*-789-AB$	$-BA-9-87^*-65-43^*21$
3922	06506	$12-34-(567^*-8-9-AB)$	$-BA9-8^*-765-(4+321)$
3923	06507	$-1-(23-4-(-56+7^*-8^*-9A-B))$	$BA+9^*-87-(65-4321)$
3924	06508	$1+234+56^*78+9A-B$	$B+A9-8+7-6+5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
3925	06509	$1^*2+34-(56^*(7-89)-A)-B$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7-6)-5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
3926	06510	$-1-(23+4)-5-(6^*-789+AB)$	$B-A-(9^*8^*-76-(5-4+3)-21)$
3927	06511	$-12-3-4+567^*8-(-9-AB)$	$B+A-(-98-(-7+6))+5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
3928	06512	$1-23-4-5-6^*-789-AB$	$-B^*(A+9+8+7-6-5-(432+1))$
3929	06513	$-12+3-(-4567+8+9^*AB)$	$BA+9-876^*-5+4^*32^*1$
392A	06514	$1-23+4567+8+9^*-AB$	$B-A+9+8+7^*654+3-2-1$
392B	06515	$-1-2+3-45-6^*-789+A^*-B$	$B-A98+(7+6)^*(5+432+1)$
3930	06516	$-12+3-4-56-(7^*8^*-9A+B)$	$-B+A-(9-8)-(-7^*654+3-21)$
3931	06517	$-1-234+5^*-67^*(-8-9)+AB$	$B-A-9-8-7^*-654+32-1$
3932	06518	$-1-23+4-(5+6^*-789+AB)$	$BA9+8-765^*-4+321$
3933	06519	$-12-34+5-6^*-789-A^*B$	$B-A-9^*8^*-76^*(5-4)-32^*-1$
3934	06520	$12-(-3-4-567^*8-9A+B)$	$B+A-9^*8^*-76-5-4+3+21$
3935	06521	$1-2^*-3^*-45+6+7^*-8^*(9-AB)$	$-BA+9-8^*76+5+4321$
3936	06522	$1+23-45-6^*-789-AB$	$B+A9-8+76^*(-5+43+21)$
3937	06523	$1-(2345-67-8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA+9-87^*-65-43^*21$
3938	06524	$1+2-3+4567-8-9^*AB$	$B+A-9-8^*(7^*6^*5-4^*(3+2))^{\wedge}1$
3939	06525	$-1-2+3+4-567^*-8+9A+B$	$B+A+98+7+6+5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
393A	06526	$-12+3456+7^*89-A-B$	$B+A+9^*8^*76+54-32-1$
393B	06527	$1-23-4+5+6^*(789-A-B)$	$BA+9^*8^*76-5^4 \cdot 4-3^*21$
3940	06528	$-1+2-(-34+5)+6^*(78+9^*-A^*-B)$	$-B+A+9^*8^*76-5+43+2+1$
3941	06529	$-1^*(-2-3-4567-(-8+9^*-AB))$	$B+A+((9+8)^7 \cdot 6+5+4)^3 \cdot 2+1$
3942	06530	$-12+3456+78^*9-A^*B$	$-B+A-(9-8)+7^*(654+3+2)+1$
3943	06531	$-1^*(2+34-5-6^*789+A^*B)$	$-B+A9-8+7^*654-3^*21$
3944	06532	$12+3-(45-6^*789)+A^*-B$	$-BA^*(9+8-(-7+6+54))-3+2+1$
3945	06533	$1-(23+4+5-6^*789)-A^*B$	$-B-(A9+87-65^*-4^*(3-21))$
3946	06534	$-1+234+5^*678+9AB$	$BA9+8+7-(-6+54^*3^*-21)$
3947	06535	$-1-2345-(-6^*-78^*(-9-A)+B)$	$B-A-(9-8-7^*654)-(-32-1)$
3948	06536	$1+234+5^*678+9AB$	$-BA-9^*8+76^*(5-4)^3 \cdot 21$
3949	06537	$12-34-(5+6^*-789)-A^*B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*654+32-1$
394A	06538	$12^*(3+4-567+89A-B)$	$B-A9-87^*-65-43^*21$
394B	06539	$-123+45+6^*789-(A+B)$	$B+A-9+8-7^*6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
3950	06540	$-12+34+567^*8-9+AB$	$B-(A9-8)+7^*(654-3+21)$
3951	06541	$-1-(-23+45+6^*-789)+A^*-B$	$BA9-(8-7^*(65+432))-1$
3952	06542	$-1-(-2-3)-4-5-(-6^*789+AB)$	$BA+98-(765-4321)$
3953	06543	$-1234-5-678^*-9^*(-A+B)$	$BA+98-76-5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 21$
3954	06544	$123+45-67^*8^*(-9A-B)$	$B-(A-9)-(8+765-4)^*-3^*-2^*-1$
3955	06545	$-12+3-(-4-5)+6^*789-AB$	$B-(A9-876^*5+4-321)$
3956	06546	$1+2-3+4-5-6^*-789-AB$	$BA9+8^*76+(5+4)^*321$
3957	06547	$1+2-3^*456+7^*(-8+9A)^*B$	$-B-(A-98^*-7)+6-(-5-4321)$
3958	06548	$-123-456-7^*-89^*A+B$	$-BA-9^*-8^*76+5^*(4-32^*-1)$
3959	06549	$12-(3-(-4-5)+6^*-789)-AB$	$BA9-8-7^*(-65-(432+1))$
395A	06550	$-12-3-4^*-5+6^*789-AB$	$BA98+7^*-65^*(43-21)$
395B	06551	$12-3+4567+8-9^*AB$	$BA9+8-7^*(-65-432+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3960	06552	$1+23+4567-8+9^*-AB$	$B-A+9^*8^*76-5+43+21$
3961	06553	$-1+2-3^*-45^*-6^*-7-89-A-B$	$-B-A^*-9^*(-8-(7-6))+5+4321$
3962	06554	$-1234+5-678^*-9-A+B$	$BA-9^*87-(6^*5-4321)$
3963	06555	$1+2+3-4-56-7^*8^*-9A+B$	$B+A^*987-65-4321$
3964	06556	$1-2^*-345^*6+7^*89^*(-A+B)$	$B^*(-A9-8-7-6+543-21)$
3965	06557	$-123-(4-5-6^*(789+A)+B)$	$BA+9^*8^*76-(54+3)-2^*-1$
3966	06558	$12+3^*-456-7^*(8-9A)^*B$	$B-A+98^*-7-(-6+5)^*4321$
3967	06559	$-1-2+3456-(-7^*89+A-B)$	$BA-98+7^*654+32-1$
3968	06560	$1-2^*(3+4)+5-6^*-789+A^*-B$	$BA-98+7^*654-32^*-1$
3969	06561	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5+6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA-98+7^*654+32+1$
396A	06562	$-12+3^*-4^*5-6^*7^*(-89+A+B)$	$BA+9^*-8-7^*(-654-3)-21$
396B	06563	$1-2^*(-3+456)-7^*-8^*(9+A+B)$	$-B-A+98+7^*654-(3+21)$
3970	06564	$1+23+4-567^*-8-(-9-AB)$	$B+A-9-8^*7^*(6+5-4^{\wedge}3^*2)^{\wedge}1$
3971	06565	$12+3-4-(-5-6^*789+A+B)$	$B+A^*-9-8^*76-5+4321$
3972	06566	$-1+23-(-4567-8+9^*AB)$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
3973	06567	$12-3+4+5-6^*-789-AB$	$B^*(A+98+765-432^*1)$
3974	06568	$1+23+4567+8-9^*AB$	$-B+A9-8-7^*-654-32^*1$
3975	06569	$-1-2+3+4+5-6^*-789-A^*B$	$B+A9+8-7^*-654-3^*21$
3976	06570	$1+(2-3+4-5+6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*-87^*-6-(-5+43)^*-21$
3977	06571	$1-234+56-7^*-8^*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A^*-9^*-87+6^*(5-(-4+321))$
3978	06572	$123-4+5^*(-6+7)^*(89A+B)$	$-BA-98+7^*-65+4321$
3979	06573	$-1+2^*-3+4^*(5^*-6^*-7+8+9AB)$	$BA+9^*-87-6-(5-4321)$
397A	06574	$1+23+4-5-6^*-789-AB$	$-B+A^*(-98-(-7-(-6+543)))$
397B	06575	$-1+2^*(345-6)^*7-(8-9)-AB$	$-B+A9-8+76+5^*43^*21$
3980	06576	$123+4567-8+9A^*-B$	$B-(A-98)+7^*654-(32-1)$
3981	06577	$-1234-567-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A-98^*7-6+5+4321$
3982	06578	$-12+3+4+5-6^*-789-AB$	$-B^*(-A9-(8+7)-6-(-5-4)-321)$
3983	06579	$123+4+567^*8-9-(-A-B)$	$-B-A^*(-987-6+543-21)$
3984	06580	$-12^*(3-(-45-6+7+8))^*(-9+A-B)$	$-B-(A-9^*-8^*-76+5^*4^*3^*-2)+1$
3985	06581	$1+234-(567^*-8+9+AB)$	$-B-A+987^*6-54^*(3+21)$
3986	06582	$1^*-2^*3^*(-4+5-6-(789-A-B))$	$-B-A9^*-8-7+654^*3^*-2^*-1$
3987	06583	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5-6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA-9-8-7^*-654-32^*1$
3988	06584	$1+2-34^*(-56+7-89)+A+B$	$-BA9+8^*(765-43)+21$
3989	06585	$-123-(45+6^*-789-AB)$	$B-A+98-7^*-65^*4^*-3^*(-2+1)$
398A	06586	$12+3+4+567^*8+9+AB$	$B+A9-8+7^*(654-(3-(-2-1)))$
398B	06587	$-12-3-4-5-(6^*-789+A)-B$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)-4+3^{\wedge}2^*1$
3990	06588	$1^*-2^*3^*(-4+5)^*(6+7+8)^*(9-AB)$	$BA9-8^*-76^*5-43^*-21$
3991	06589	$1+2^*34^*-56+78^*(9A+B)$	$-B^*(-A98+7-(-654-(-3+21)))$
3992	06590	$123-456^*(7-8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A+98-7^*-654^*(3-2)-1$
3993	06591	$-1-(2-3)-(4^*5^*6^*-7^*8+9A+B)$	$B+A^*(-9-8)+7-(-6+5)^*(-432+1)$
3994	06592	$123+4567+8+9A^*-B$	$-B+A^*-9+(87-6)^*(-54-3-2)^*-1$
3995	06593	$-1+23+4^*5-6^*-789-AB$	$B+A+9-8-7^*-654+3^*21$
3996	06594	$-1-2-3+4-5-6^*-789-AB$	$B+A-9-(8+765+4)^*(-3-2-1)$
3997	06595	$1-2^*3-(-4-5+6)-(-7^*8^*9A+B)$	$BA9-8+76+54^*-3^*-21$
3998	06596	$1^*2-3+4+5-(6^*(-789+A)-B)$	$B+A+98+7^*654-32+1$
3999	06597	$-1-23-45+6^*789^*(-A+B)$	$B+A9-8+76-5^*43^*-21$
399A	06598	$-1-(23+4+5^*-6^*(78-(-9A-B)))$	$B+A-(-98-7^*(654-3+2^*-1))$
399B	06599	$1+234+567^*8+9-AB$	$BA-9+8+7^*654+32^*-1$
39A0	06600	$-1-(2-3-4-5-6^*789)-AB$	$B^*-A^*(98-76+5-43)^*(2+1)$
39A1	06601	$123+4567-89A-B$	$B-A9^*(-8+7)^*-6-(5-4321)$
39A2	06602	$1234+5-6^*7^*-89+AB$	$B-A^*-987-6^*5-4321$
39A3	06603	$-1^*(-23-4)^*(5-6-(-78+9-AB))$	$B+A+9^*(8-7/-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-(3+2))^{\wedge}1)$
39A4	06604	$-1+2+3+4-5-6^*-789-AB$	$BA+9^*-8+(765+4)^*-3^*-2^*1$
39A5	06605	$-1^*(-2-3-4+5+6^*-789+AB)$	$B+A-(-98+7^*-654-(-3-21))$
39A6	06606	$12+3+4+5+6^*789-AB$	$-B-(A9-87^*-6+5)+4321$
39A7	06607	$12+3+4-5+6^*7^*-8^*9A+B$	$B+A98-7^*6^*5^*-4^*3^*2^*1$
39A8	06608	$-1-(-23+456)-7^*8^*(-9A-B)$	$B-A+98-7^*-654-3-2^*1$
39A9	06609	$-1-2^*-3+4+5+6^*(78+9+A-B)$	$BA-9+8-7^*-654-3-21$
39AA	06610	$-12+3+4+5+6^*7^*(8+9)-AB$	$-BA+9^*-8^*(-76-5)-4^*(-3+21)$
39AB	06611	$12+3+4+5+6^*(789-A-B)$	$-B-A9^*-8^*7+6+5-432+1$
39B0	06612	$-1-2-3+4+5+6^*7+8+9^*-AB$	$B+A+(987-(65+4))^*(3+2)+1$
39B1	06613	$-1+2-3+4-5-(-6^*789+A)-B$	$-B+A+987^*-6-5+4321$
39B2	06614	$-1-2^*-3+4^*5-6-7+8+9AB$	$BA+9-8-7^*65^*4^*-3+2+1$
39B3	06615	$12-3^*(45+67)^*(-8-9)-AB$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)+4^{\wedge}3/2+1$
39B4	06616	$-1+2-3+4+5+6^*-7+89^*-AB$	$-B+A9+8-7^*-654+3^*-2^*1$
39B5	06617	$123+4567-(89+A)^*B$	$BA9-8^*(-7-6)-54^*-3^*21$
39B6	06618	$1-(2-3+4+5)+6-(-7^*-8^*-9A-B)$	$B-A+98+7^*654+3+2^*1$
39B7	06619	$12-(3+4+5)^*(-6-7+8+9AB)$	$BA+9-(-8-(-76+5))^*(-43-21))$
39B8	06620	$-1+2+3+4^*(-5^*-6+7+8+9A-B)$	$-B+A+98-7^*-654-3^*(-2-1)$
39B9	06621	$12-(-3+4-5-6-7^*8^*9A+B)$	$B+A+9-(-8-76)^*(54+3)+21$
39BA	06622	$-1^*(-2-(3+4-5-6)^*7^*(-8+9-(-A-B)))$	$B+A9-(8-7^*654)+3^*2^*-1$
39BB	06623	$123+4567-89A+B$	$-BA+9-87^*6-(-5-4321)$
3A00	06624	$-1+2+3+4+5-6^*(78-9A)^*-B$	$B-(-A-98+7^*-654)+3^*(-2-1)$
3A01	06625	$1+2-3-4+5-6^*7^*(-8-9)^*-A-B$	$-BA+9+8+7+(6+5)^*(432-1)$
3A02	06626	$-1+2^*3+4^*5-6-7^*-8^*-9-A-B$	$-B-A-98+7^*(654+32)+1$
3A03	06627	$1-(-2-3-(4-5-6^*-789+A^*-B))$	$B+A+98-7^*-654+3^*-2^*1$
3A04	06628	$1+23+4+5+6^*789-AB$	$-BA+9-8-7^*(-654-32-1)$
3A05	06629	$-1+2+3-4+5+6^*789^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A9-(-8+7^*-654-3^*2-1)$
3A06	06630	$-123+4+5+6^*(78+9)+AB$	$-BA+9-(-8+7^*(-654-32+1))$
3A07	06631	$-1-2+3-4+5+6^*(789-A+B)$	$B+A-9^*8^*-76-5^*(-4+3-21)$
3A08	06632	$-1^*2^*(3+4+5+6^*(78+9A^*B))$	$BA+98-7+6+5^*-43^*-21$
3A09	06633	$1-(23+4+5-6^*7^*(8+9+AB))$	$B^*(A-98+76+5-432^*-1)$
3A0A	06634	$1^*(2+3+4+5-6-78)^*(8+9+AB)$	$BA-9^*(8+76)+5+4321$
3A0B	06635	$-12+3-4-5-6^*-789+A+B$	$-BA-9^*(-8+7-6-543+21)$
3A10	06636	$-1-2+3+4-5+6^*(7-8+9)+AB$	$-B+A-(-9-87)-(-6+5^*43)^*-21$
3A11	06637	$123-4+5+6^*(6-7+8-9A-B)$	$BA+9^*87-654^*-3^*-2^*-1$
3A12	06638	$123-4+5+6^*7^*8-9^*-A-B$	$B-A9+87^*-6+5+4321$
3A13	06639	$-123-(4-5-6^*789)+AB$	$B+A+98+7^*654+3+2+1$
3A14	06640	$-1-2-3-4-5-6^*-789+A+B$	$B-A-98+7^*(654+32-1)$
3A15	06641	$1+2^*3+4+5+6^*7^*-8^*(-9A+B)$	$BA+9-(8+7^*-654-3+2-1)$
3A16	06642	$1^*2^*3^*(-4+5-6^*-7-8^*9)+AB$	$-B-(A-9+8^*76-5-4321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3A17	06643	$12+3456-(78-(9+A))^*-B$	$-B-A9^*-8^*-7+6^*-543*(-2-1)$
3A18	06644	$-1-23+4567-89^*A+B$	$-B+A-9-8^*76+5+4321$
3A19	06645	$1+2-3^*(4-567+8-9AB)$	$B-A+(987-6-54)^*(3+2)-1$
3A1A	06646	$-1-2-(3+4^*5-6^*(789+A-B))$	$BA+9-8-7^*-654-3^*-2+1$
3A1B	06647	$-1+23-(4-45-(6^*789-A^*B))$	$B+A-9^*(-8+76)-5+4321$
3A20	06648	$1^*-2^*(-3+4^*(5-678+9A)+B)$	$-B+A+98-7^*-654+32-1$
3A21	06649	$1+23+45^*(6+78)+9AB$	$BA-9^*-8^*76+54-(32-1)$
3A22	06650	$12^*(3-(4-5+678-9AB))$	$B-A+987-6^*-5^*(4+3)^*21$
3A23	06651	$-1-23-(4-567+8^*(9A+B))$	$-B-(A-9)-(-876^*5-(-4+321))$
3A24	06652	$1-23-(4-(5+6^*789)-(A-B))$	$BA-9^*8^*-76+5+(-4+3)^*-21$
3A25	06653	$-12-(3+4+5)+6^*789-(A-B)$	$B+A+9^*(8+(7+6^*5-4^*3)^*2)-1$
3A26	06654	$-1+2+3+4567+89^*-A-B$	$B-(A+98)-7^*(-654-32-1)$
3A27	06655	$1-23-(4-56)-(7^*8^*9A-B)$	$B^*(-A-9-(8-765-4+321))$
3A28	06656	$-1-2^*3^*(-4+5+6-789)-(-A-B)$	$-B+A987+65^*4^*(-32-1)$
3A29	06657	$-12-(3456+7^*-89+A^*-B)$	$BA9+87^*(-6+5+43+2^*-1)$
3A2A	06658	$-1-23-(4-5^*(67+89A-B))$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7)^*(-6+5^*4)^*3^*2+1$
3A2B	06659	$1+23^*45^*-6-(7-89AB)$	$-B-(A9-8)-(-7^*654-32)-1$
3A30	06660	$-1-(23-4)-(-5-6+7^*-8^*9A-B)$	$-B+A9+8+7^*654-32^*-1$
3A31	06661	$-12+3+4567-89^*A+B$	$BA9+8+(76+5)^*(43+2-1)$
3A32	06662	$-12-(3-4567-8^*(9A-B))$	$BA+9^*-8^*-76+5-4-(-32-1)$
3A33	06663	$-1234+567+8^*9^*A^*B$	$B+A+9^*(8-7+6+(5+4)^3+2/1)$
3A34	06664	$12^*(345-6-7-8-9+A+B)$	$-BA+9-87+6^*(-5+43)^*21$
3A35	06665	$123-45-6^*-789-AB$	$B+A^*9^*-8^*(7-6)+5+4321$
3A36	06666	$-1+234+5^*(6-7)^*-89A-B$	$B-A9^*8+7+6^*(5+43^*21)$
3A37	06667	$12-3-(4+5)+6^*789-(A+B)$	$-BA9-8^*-765+4^*-3^*21$
3A38	06668	$-12+3^*45^*-6^*-7-8-9+A+B$	$B+A-(-9^*8^*76+54^*-3+21)$
3A39	06669	$1^*-23^*(-45-(67+8+9A)+B)$	$BA-9^*8^*(-7-65-(4+3))-21$
3A3A	06670	$-12+3-(45-6+7-89)^*AB$	$B+A^*-98-(76^*-5-4321)$
3A3B	06671	$-1-2+34+5+6^*(789-A)+B$	$-BA9+87^*65-4+321$
3A40	06672	$-1+23-(45+6^*-789-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8+7^*(654-3+21)$
3A41	06673	$1-23+4^*5-(6^*-789+A-B)$	$B+A-9^*8+(7+6+5+4^*3)^2^*1$
3A42	06674	$-1-2+345+6^*(-7-89^*-A-B)$	$BA^*(9+87+6+5-43-21)$
3A43	06675	$-1-2^*34-5^*(-67-89A)+B$	$-B+A9^*8^*7-65-(4+321)$
3A44	06676	$-12+3+45+(-6-7^*8)^*(-9A+B)$	$BA+9-8+7^*654-(-32+1)$
3A45	06677	$12-3-(4-5+6^*-789+A)-B$	$BA+9-(8+7^*-654+32^*-1)$
3A46	06678	$-1-(2-3)-(-4+5)-6^*-789-A+B$	$B-(-A987-65^*4^*(32+1))$
3A47	06679	$12-3^*-4^*(-5-6^*-78)+9^*A+B$	$-B+A+9-876^*-5+4+321$
3A48	06680	$1+2^*34-56^*(7-89)+AB$	$BA9-876^*(-5-(-4+3))-(-2-1)$
3A49	06681	$12-3-4-5+6^*789-(A-B)$	$B-A-9-8^*(76-5)+4321$
3A4A	06682	$-1-2-(3-4-(5-6^*-789)-(-A+B))$	$-B-A9-8-7^*65+4321$
3A4B	06683	$-1-23-4-5^*-67^*(-8-9)^*(A-B)$	$BA+9+8+7^*(654+3+2-1)$
3A50	06684	$12+34-5^*-6^*(78+9A+B)$	$B+A-(-9-8^*-76-5-4321)$
3A51	06685	$1-23-4+5^*6+7^*(8^*9A+B)$	$-B-A9-876^*-5-(-432-1)$
3A52	06686	$-12+3-456-7^*-89^*A-B$	$B+A-(-9+87^*-65+43^*21)$
3A53	06687	$-1-2+3^*(-4-(-567-8-9AB))$	$-BA-9+8+7^*-65+4321$
3A54	06688	$-12+3+456^*7+89^*(A+B)$	$-B^*(-A+9)^*-8^*(-76+5+4+3+2^*1)$
3A55	06689	$-1-2+3456-7^*-89+AB$	$BA+98^*-7^*-6-(54+3)^*-21$
3A56	06690	$-1-(-2-(3456+7))-8^*(-9A+B)$	$B+A+9^*(8+7-6+(5+4)^3+2+1)$
3A57	06691	$-12+345-6^*-789+AB$	$B+A^*(9+87)^*6+5^*(-4-3-2+1)$
3A58	06692	$1^*2-3^*(4-(567+8)-9AB)$	$-BA-(-9-876^*5)-(-432-1)$
3A59	06693	$-1+23-(4-56)-7^*8^*-9A-B$	$-B-A-98-7^*65+4321$
3A5A	06694	$-1+2-3^*4+5^*(6-(78-9AB))$	$BA+9+8+7^*654+32+1$
3A5B	06695	$-123+4+5^*6-7^*8^*(9-AB)$	$-BA-98-7^*-654+321$
3A60	06696	$-12-(3+4^*5)-6^*(789-A)-B$	$BA-(9+8)-7^*-654-3^*-21$
3A61	06697	$12-(3-(4+5+6^*789)-(A-B))$	$-B+A9^*(-87-6+5-4^*(-32-1))$
3A62	06698	$1+23-4-5+6^*789-A+B$	$B-A9^*8^*-7-(65-432)^*-1$
3A63	06699	$-12-3-(-456-78)^*9-A^*-B$	$-B^*(A9+87-6^*54-321)$
3A64	06700	$1+2+3-(-4-5^*(67+89A-B))$	$B+A-9-8^*(-76-543+21)$
3A65	06701	$1-2+34+5-(-6^*789+A+B)$	$BA+98+7^*-65^*4^*-3-21$
3A66	06702	$-12-3-(456+7^*-89^*A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*7-65+432^*-1)$
3A67	06703	$12+3456+7-8^*(9A+B)$	$B-(-A9-(-8+7^*654+3^*21))$
3A68	06704	$-1+23+4-5-6^*-789-(A-B)$	$B+A-9-8^*7^*(-6^*5^*4^*3+2)^*1$
3A69	06705	$-12+34-5-6^*(-789+A-B)$	$-BA9+87^*(65+4)+3^*21$
3A6A	06706	$1^*-2^*(-3-4)^*(5^*6+7+89-(A+B))$	$BA9+876^*(5-4+3)+21$
3A6B	06707	$-1-2-(3-4567-(-8-9^*A^*B))$	$B-A+9876^*5+432+1$
3A70	06708	$-1+234+567^*8+(-9A)^*-B$	$-B-A+9+8^*7^*6^*-5^*-4^*(3+2^*-1)$
3A71	06709	$12-3^*45^*6^*-7+8-9^*(A-B)$	$B+A^*987+65-4321$
3A72	06710	$-12+3456-78-9^*A^*B$	$-B^*(A9-(-8+7-(6-543+21)))$
3A73	06711	$123+4567+8+9^*-AB$	$-BA9+8^*(765-(4+3+21))$
3A74	06712	$-12-(3-4567)+8-9^*A^*B$	$-B-A9-8^*-765-4^*321$
3A75	06713	$123+4^*5+6^*(-78+9^*AB)$	$-B+A-98+7^*-65+4321$
3A76	06714	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4-5+6+789-(A-B))$	$BA+9-8+7^*654-3^*-21$
3A77	06715	$12+345-6^*-7^*(8+9+AB)$	$BA+98-7^*-654-(32+1)$
3A78	06716	$12+34+5-6^*-789-(A+B)$	$-B-A+9^*8^*76+5^*43+2^*1$
3A79	06717	$-123-4^*(5-6+78-9)^*(-A-B)$	$BA-(-98-7^*654+32-1)$
3A7A	06718	$1+23+4^*5^*-6^*7^*-8-(9A+B)$	$BA-98-7^*(-654-(3+21))$
3A7B	06719	$123-4-(-5-(6^*789-AB))$	$B-A9^*(-8+7-65+43-21)$
3A80	06720	$-12-3+45+6^*(789-A+B)$	$B+A9^*8^*7+6-54-321$
3A81	06721	$12-3+45+6^*789-(A+B)$	$B-A^*9+8^*(76-(5+43))^*21$
3A82	06722	$-1+2+3+(45+6)^*(7+89)-A^*-B$	$-BA-9^*8^*-76-54^*3^*2^*-1$
3A83	06723	$-1-(-23+456)-(-7^*89^*A+B)$	$BA+98+76-5^*43^*-21$
3A84	06724	$-1+23+4+5^*(-6-7)^*-89-AB$	$BA-(-98+7^*-65^*4^*3)+2^*-1$
3A85	06725	$-1+23-456^*-7-89^*(A-B)$	$BA+98+7^*65^*-4^*-3-(2-1)$
3A86	06726	$-1^*2^*-3^*(-4+5+6+789+A+B)$	$-B-A-9-87^*6+5+4321$
3A87	06727	$1+23-(4-5)^*6^*789-(A-B)$	$BA98-7-6^*5^*(4+321)$
3A88	06728	$-1-(23-4567+8^*9A+B)$	$BA+9^*(8-76-5)+4321$
3A89	06729	$1234+5^*678-9A+B$	$-BA-98^*7-6^*-5+4321$
3A8A	06730	$12-34-5^*(-67-89A)+B$	$BA+9-(-8+7^*-654+3^*-21)$
3A8B	06731	$-123+4+56+7^*-8^*(9-AB)$	$BA+9^*8-7^*(-654-3)^*(2-1)$
3A90	06732	$-1-2+3+45-6^*-789-A+B$	$-BA+987-(65-4)^*3^*-21$
3A91	06733	$1+234-567^*-8-(9-A)+B$	$-BA9-8+765+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3A92	06734	$12 * (-345 - (-678 - 9 + A - B))$	$-B - A - (-9 - 87 * 6) - 5 + 4321$
3A93	06735	$1 + 2 - 3 + 4567 - 8 * (-9 + AB)$	$-BA + 9 * 8 * (76 + 5) - (-4 * 3 - 21)$
3A94	06736	$12 - 3 + 45 - 6 * (-789 - A + B)$	$-BA - 9 - (-87 + 6) * (-5 + 43 + 21)$
3A95	06737	$1 - 2 + 3 - (-4567 - 8 * (9 - AB))$	$-B - A - (9 * 8 + 7 * 65) + 4321$
3A96	06738	$-12 + 3456 - 7 + 8 * 9A - B$	$B - A - (9 + 87 * 6) - 5 + 4321$
3A97	06739	$-12 - 34 - (-5 + 6 * -789) + A * B$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 + 3 * 2 + 1$
3A98	06740	$1 + 234 * 5 - 6 * 78 * 9 + AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 - 3 * 2 - 1$
3A99	06741	$12 + 34 - 56 * (-78 - 9) + A + B$	$BA98 + 7 - 6 * 5 * (4 + 321)$
3A9A	06742	$-1 - 2 - 345 + 6 + 7 * 8 * (9A + B)$	$-BA9 + 87 - 654 * 3 * (-2 - 1)$
3A9B	06743	$-12 - 34 + 56 * (78 + 9) + AB$	$B * (A98 - (-7 + 654) - (-3 + 21))$
3AA0	06744	$-1 * -2 * -3 * (4 - (-5 + 6) - 7 - 8 * (9 + AB))$	$-B - A + 9 - 87 * 6 + 5 + 4321$
3AA1	06745	$-12 + 3 - 45 + 6 * 789 + AB$	$B - A - 9 - (-87 * (6 + 54) + 321)$
3AA2	06746	$1 - (-23 + 4 - (-5 - 6 * (-789 - A) - B))$	$-BA + 9 + 87 + 65 * 4 * (3 - 21)$
3AA3	06747	$-1 + 234 - 5 * 6 * (-78 + 9 - AB)$	$BA + 98 + 7 * (654 - 3 + 2) * 1$
3AA4	06748	$123 + 4 + 5 + 6 * 789 - A * B$	$BA - 9 * -8 + (765 + 4) * -3 * 2 * -1$
3AA5	06749	$-1 + 234 - 567 * -8 + 9 + A + B$	$-BA9 + 8 + 765 + 4321$
3AA6	06750	$-1 * 23 * (-4 - 5 - 6 * -7 - 8) * (-9 + A - B)$	$-B - A * -9 + 87 * 6 * 5 + 4 + 321$
3AA7	06751	$-123 - 456 * 7 - 8 * -9A - B$	$-B - A * -9 * (-8 + 76) - 5 - 432 + 1$
3AA8	06752	$1 - 2 - (3 - 4567) - 8 * 9A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 + 3 - 2 + 1$
3AA9	06753	$-1 + 2 + 3456 - 7 - 8 * -9A - B$	$BA + 98 + 7 * 654 - 3 - 2 * -1$
3AAA	06754	$-1 - (-2 + 34 - 5 + 6 * -789) + A * B$	$BA - (-98 + 7 * -654) - 3 + 2 + 1$
3AAB	06755	$-1 * (-23 - (4 - 56)) * (-78 - 9 * A - B)$	$B + A * 9 * 8 - (-76 - 5) + 4321$
3AB0	06756	$1 - (-2 + 3) - 45 - (6 * -789 - AB)$	$B - (A - 9) + 87 * 6 - 5 + 4321$
3AB1	06757	$1 + 2 + 34 + 5 * -67 * (-8 - 9) + A - B$	$B + A * 9 - 87 * 65 - 43 * 21$
3AB2	06758	$-1234 - 5 - (-6 + 7 * (-89A + B))$	$B - A9 + 87 * (6 + 54 - 3) - 21$
3AB3	06759	$12 + 34 + 5 * (6 - (78 - 9AB))$	$-BA9 + 8 * (765 - 4 + 3 - 21)$
3AB4	06760	$-12 - (34 - 5 - 6 * 789 - AB)$	$BA9 + 87 * (6 - 5) * (43 - 2) * 1$
3AB5	06761	$-12 - 3 - (-4567 - (8 * -9A + B))$	$B - A9 + 87 - 65 * 4 * (3 - 21)$
3AB6	06762	$-1 * 2 * -3 * (-45 - 67 + 89A - B)$	$-B + A98 * 7 - 6 + (5 + 4) * -321$
3AB7	06763	$1 + 23 + 4567 + 8 * (9 - AB)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 * 3) * 2 + 1$
3AB8	06764	$1 + 234 + 5 * (6 + 7) * (8 - (9 - A)) * B$	$-B + A + 9 - (-87 * 6 - 5 - 4321)$
3AB9	06765	$-1 + 2 - (-3456 + 78 * 9) - A * -B$	$B * (A9 + 8 + 7 + 654 - 321)$
3ABA	06766	$12 - (-3456 + 7) + 8 * 9A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 + 7 * (654 + 32) * 1$
3ABB	06767	$-12 - (-3 - 4567 + 8 * 9A - B)$	$-B + A * 9 + 8 * (76 + 543 - 21)$
3B00	06768	$1 * 2 + 3456 + 7 - 8 * -9A - B$	$B + A9 + 8 * (7 + 6) * 54 - 3 - 21$
3B01	06769	$-1234 - 56 + 7 * 89A + B$	$BA9 - 8 * (-765 - 4 + 321)$
3B02	06770	$-1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 * (-67 - (-8 - 9AB))$	$-B + A + 9 + (-8 - 76) * (54 + 3 + 2) * -1$
3B03	06771	$-12 + 3456 - 78 * -9 + AB$	$-B - (A9 + 8 * (7 - 654) + 321)$
3B04	06772	$-12 - 34 + 5 * (-6 - 7) * -89 - A + B$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7) * (-6 + 5 + 43) + 2 - 1$
3B05	06773	$1 - 2 - 34 + 5 - 6 * -789 + AB$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) * 3) + 2 / 1$
3B06	06774	$-12 + 3456 + 7 - 8 * -9A + B$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) * 3) + 2 + 1$
3B07	06775	$123 - 45 - 6 * -789 - A - B$	$-B + A9 * 8 * 7 - (-65 + 4) * -3 * 2 * -1$
3B08	06776	$1234 + 5 * (678 - (9 + A) - B)$	$BA + 98 * -7 + 65 + 4321$
3B09	06777	$1 + 2 + 3456 - 7 - 8 * -9A + B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * (7 * 6 * 5 * 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$
3B0A	06778	$12 - 34 - 5 - 6 * -789 + AB$	$-BA + 987 * (6 - 5 + 4) - 3 * 21$
3B0B	06779	$-1 * (2 - 3 - 4567 - 8 * -9A - B)$	$-B + A * (9 - 8 - 76 + 543 - 2 - 1)$
3B10	06780	$1 - 2 - (-3 - 4567 - (8 * -9A + B))$	$-B + A9 * 8 + 76 * 54 - (3 - 2 * 1)$
3B11	06781	$-1 - 2 + 3 * -45 * -6 * 7 + 89 - (A - B)$	$-B + A9 - 876 * -5 - 4 + 321$
3B12	06782	$-1 - 2 - (-3456 + 78 * 9 - AB)$	$BA + 98 + 7 * 654 - (-3 - 21)$
3B13	06783	$123 + 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 * -8 * 9A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 * 5 - 4 * (3 + 2 * 1)$
3B14	06784	$1 + 23 - 45 + 6 * 789 + AB$	$-BA + 9 * -87 + 65 * 43 * 2 - 1$
3B15	06785	$-12 + 34 * -56 + 7 - 8 * 9 * -AB$	$-BA - 9 * 87 + 65 * -43 * -2 * 1$
3B16	06786	$12 + 34 + 56 * (-7 + 8 - 9 + A * B)$	$-BA + 9 * -87 + 65 * -43 * -2 + 1$
3B17	06787	$1 * (23 - (456 - (7 - 8) - (9 - A))) * -B$	$-B * (A - 9 * -8 - 76 + 5 + 432 * -1)$
3B18	06788	$12 - 34 + 5 - 6 * -789 + AB$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 - 4 * 3) * 2 / 1$
3B19	06789	$-123 + 4 * 5 * -6 * (-7 - 8 * 9 - (A - B))$	$B + A - (-98 - 7) * (-6 + 54 - 3) - (-2 - 1)$
3B1A	06790	$-1 * 2 * (34 - 5) * (-67 - 8 - 9 + A - B)$	$-BA9 + 87 - 6 * (5 + 43) * -21$
3B1B	06791	$1 + 2 + 3456 - (-7 + 8 * -9A) + B$	$BA + 9 * -8 * -76 + 5 * (-4 + 32) - 1$
3B20	06792	$123 + 45 + 6 * 789 - A * B$	$BA + 98 + 7 * 654 - 32 * -1$
3B21	06793	$-1234 - 5 * 6 + 7 * 89A - B$	$B + A9 * 8 * 7 + 6 - (-5 - 4 + 321)$
3B22	06794	$-12 + 3456 + 789 - AB$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 76 * 5 + 4321$
3B23	06795	$123 - (45 - 6 * 789) - (-A + B)$	$-B - A - (9 + 87 * 6 - 5 - 432 - 1)$
3B24	06796	$-1 * (-23 + 4 * -5 - 6 * (789 + A) - B)$	$BA - 9 - 876 * -5 - 4 + 321$
3B25	06797	$123 - 4 + 5 - (-6 + 7 * -8 * 9A - B)$	$B + A9 * 8 - 76 * -54 + 3 * 2 * -1$
3B26	06798	$1 + 2 - 3 * -4 - 5 - 6 * -789 - A * -B$	$B * (-A9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 543 - (2 + 1))$
3B27	06799	$1 + 2 * -3 * (-4 + 5) + 6 * (789 + A + B)$	$-B + A - 9 - 8 * (-7 + 65) + 4321$
3B28	06800	$-1 * (23 + 45) * (6 - 7 - 89 + A + B)$	$-BA - 9 * 8 * 7 + 65 + 4321$
3B29	06801	$-12 - 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 * 789 + AB$	$BA9 - 8 * (7 - 65 * -4 + 3) * -2 * 1$
3B2A	06802	$-1 + (-2 - 3 / 4 + 5) * -6 * -7 * 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B + A - 98 + 76 * -5 + 4321$
3B2B	06803	$1 - 2 + 3 + 4 - 56 * (-78 - 9) + AB$	$B + A9 - (876 * -5 + 4) + 321$
3B30	06804	$-12 * -3 * (-4 - 56 + 78 + 9 + AB)$	$B - A - (98 + 76 * 5 - 4321)$
3B31	06805	$-1 - (2 - 3456 - (789 - AB))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 - 4 * 3) * 2 - 1$
3B32	06806	$1 + 23 + 4567 + 8 * -9A + B$	$-B + A9 + 8 * (76 + 543 - 21)$
3B33	06807	$1 - 2 - (-3456 - 789) - AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 * 4 + 3) * 2 + 1$
3B34	06808	$123 - 4 + 5 + 67 * (89 - A - B)$	$-BA9 - 87 - 65 * -4 * (3 + 21)$
3B35	06809	$-1 + 2 - (-3456 - 789) - AB$	$-B * (-A9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 543 - 2) * -1$
3B36	06810	$1 * 2 - (-3456 - 789) - AB$	$-B - A - (-9 + 8 + 7 * 65 - 4321)$
3B37	06811	$12 - 3 - (4 - (-5 - 6 * -789)) + AB$	$-BA - 987 - 654 * -3 * (2 + 1)$
3B38	06812	$(-1 * 23 - (-4 + 5) + 67 - 8 + 9) * AB$	$-BA + 9 - (8 + 7 * -654 - 321)$
3B39	06813	$-1234 + 56 - 7 * (-89A + B)$	$B - (A9 + 87 + 65 * 4 * (3 - 21))$
3B3A	06814	$-12 - (34 + 5) - 67 * (-8 - 9 * A + B)$	$-B + A9 * -8 * -7 - 6 + 54 - 321$
3B3B	06815	$-1 + 23 - 4 * 5 - 6 * -789 + AB$	$B - (A9 + 87 * 6 - 5 - 432 + 1)$
3B40	06816	$-1 * -2 * -3 * (4 + 56 + 78 - 9A * B)$	$-BA * (9 + 8 - 7 - 65 + 4 * (3 + 2) - 1)$
3B41	06817	$-12 + 3456 + 7 + 8 * 9 * A * B$	$B + A + 9 * 8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 * 3) * 2 * 1$
3B42	06818	$-1 + 23 - 4 + (-56 + 7) * (-89 - A) + B$	$-B - (A9 - 87) - (-6 - 5 - 4) * 321$
3B43	06819	$123 - (4 + 5) + 6 * 789 - (A + B)$	$-B - A9 - (8 - 76) * -5 + 4321$
3B44	06820	$12 + 3 - (-4 + 5) + 6 * (789 + A + B)$	$-B * -A * (98 - 76 + 54 - (3 + 21))$
3B45	06821	$-1 - 2 - 345 - 6 - 7 * (-89 + A) * B$	$-BA9 - 8 * 76 - 5432 * -1$
3B46	06822	$12 - (-3456 - 789 + AB)$	$-BA9 + 8 * -76 + 5432 + 1$
3B47	06823	$-12 + 34 + 56 * (78 + 9) + AB$	$-BA + 9 - 8 * -7 + 6 * (-5 + 43) * 21$
3B48	06824	$-12 - (3 - 45 + 6 * -789 + A * -B)$	$B + A - 98 + 76 * -5 + 4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
3B49	06825	$12 - (-3 - (4-5) - (6*789+AB))$	$-BA+987-654*-3*2*1$
3B4A	06826	$-1+2+3456+(-78-9)*-A-B$	$-B+A9*(-87-6+5+43)*(-2+1)$
3B4B	06827	$123+4-5-6*-789-A-B$	$B-A9-8+7*654+321$
3B50	06828	$1-2+3456+789-A*B$	$-BA+9+8-(-7*654-321)$
3B51	06829	$1-23-(-4567-8*(-9A+B))$	$B+A9-8*(76-5)+4321$
3B52	06830	$1+2+34-56*(7+8-9A)-B$	$B-A-(9-8-7*-65)+4321$
3B53	06831	$-12+3-4-5*-6*7*(8+9)+AB$	$B*(-A9-87+654+3*-21)$
3B54	06832	$-123+45*6+7*(8*9A+B)$	$-B-A9+(87+6)*54-3-2+1$
3B55	06833	$-1+2*34*(5+67)-8-9+AB$	$-BA9+87*65+432+1$
3B56	06834	$-1+23*-4*56-7+89A*B$	$B+A-(9+8+7*65)+4321$
3B57	06835	$1-2-3*-45+6*789-(-A+B)$	$-B+A9*8*7-6*54-3*-2*1$
3B58	06836	$-12-3*4*-56*7+8-9A*-B$	$B-(-A+9+87*6*-5)+432*1$
3B59	06837	$123+4567+(-89+A)*B$	$B-A+98+7*6*5*(-4-3-21)$
3B5A	06838	$-1-23*-4*(56+7)-(-89-A)*B$	$B-A-98+7*654+321$
3B5B	06839	$-1+2+3+4+5-6-7*-8*(-9+AB)$	$-B-A*9*8+765*(4+3)-21$
3B60	06840	$-123*4*(-5+6+7-8-9+A-B)$	$B+A*(9-8)*(-76+543+2)-1$
3B61	06841	$-1+23*4+5*(67+89A)-B$	$B+A+9+8+7*6^5/4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
3B62	06842	$123+4-5-6*(-789-A+B)$	$-B*(A9+8-7-6-543+21)$
3B63	06843	$12+3456+789-A*B$	$B-A9+8+7*654+321$
3B64	06844	$1234+5*6*7+8+9A-B$	$B+A-9-8*-7/6*((5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
3B65	06845	$1-2*-345-6*(-7+8+9*-A)*B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7)/-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1$
3B66	06846	$12*(-3-(456-789)+A+B)$	$BA9-876+5*-43*-21$
3B67	06847	$1234-5*-6*7+8(9-A)*-B$	$-BA-9*-8*76+5*43*2-1$
3B68	06848	$123-4*-5+6*789-A-B$	$-B+A98+76*54-321$
3B69	06849	$1*(23+456+78)*9*(-A+B)$	$-BA-9*-8*76+5*-43*-2+1$
3B6A	06850	$-12-3*-4*5-6*(-789-A-B)$	$-B-A+98+7*(654+32-1)$
3B6B	06851	$123-4+5-(-6*789-(-A+B))$	$B+A*9*(-87+65-4*3)*2*-1$
3B70	06852	$1-(-23+4*-5+6*(-789-A-B))$	$BA9*(-8+7)*(-6+5+4+3+2)*-1$
3B71	06853	$1*(2-3)*(-4*-5*6*(78-9A)+B)$	$-B*(A-9-876+5+432-1)$
3B72	06854	$1*(-23+4)*(-56-78-9-AB)$	$BA+9*-8*7*-6+(-5+43)*21$
3B73	06855	$-1-(2+34)-(-56-7*8*(-9+AB))$	$-BA9+8*7*(65+43+21)$
3B74	06856	$123-4+5+6*(789-A+B)$	$B+A*-9*-87+6-54*32+1$
3B75	06857	$123+4-(-5+6*-789)-(-A+B)$	$-B-(-A-9+8*(7+6))*5-4321$
3B76	06858	$1-2-3+45-6*-789+AB$	$B+A-98+7*654+321$
3B77	06859	$-1+234+56*7*8+9+AB$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*6)*-5*-4*3-2^{\wedge}1$
3B78	06860	$123+45+6*7*(89-A-B)$	$-B+A-(-9+8*765)-4*321$
3B79	06861	$-1+2-345+6*7*8*9A-B$	$B+A-9-8-(7-6-5*4)^{\wedge}3-2*1$
3B7A	06862	$-1-(2-3-45)-(-6*-789-AB)$	$B-A-(-9+8*765)-4*321$
3B7B	06863	$1*2-(-34+5+6+7*8*(9-AB))$	$-B-A9+87+6*(-5+43)*21$
3B80	06864	$-1*2*-3*4*5(-6)*7(8-9A)*B$	$B*(-A+9*-8-(76-543-21))$
3B81	06865	$12-34*5*-6*-7+89AB$	$-BA9+8*765-43*-2*-1$
3B82	06866	$-12+3456-7-89*-A+B$	$B+A-9-8-(7-6-5*4)^{\wedge}3+2+1$
3B83	06867	$1*2+34+5*(-6-7*8+9AB)$	$-BA9+8-7+6*(-5+43)*21$
3B84	06868	$-1+2+(-3-4)*(-5+6-789+AB)$	$B-(-A-9-8)+7*-65+4321$
3B85	06869	$-1+234-5-6*-789-AB$	$B+A-9-(8+7-6*5-4)^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}1$
3B86	06870	$123+456*7+89*(A+B)$	$B+A98+76*54-321$
3B87	06871	$1+234-5-6*-789-AB$	$-BA+9+8*7*(6+54-3+2-1)$
3B88	06872	$12-34+56+7*8*(-9+AB)$	$B-(-A-987*6+543*2+1)$
3B89	06873	$-12+3*-456+7*(89A-B)$	$B+A-9-(8+7-6*5-4)^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}1$
3B8A	06874	$12*(-345-6+789-AB)$	$-B+A9-8*7*6+5+4321$
3B8B	06875	$1+2*(34+5)*67-(89+AB)$	$-B*(A-(9-(-8+7-(-6-5)))-432))*-1$
3B90	06876	$1-2*(-3/-4+5+6*7)*-8*9+AB$	$-B+A+98-7*(-654-32)-1$
3B91	06877	$1-2+(-3-4*5*6)*-7*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A+98+7*(654+32)*1$
3B92	06878	$-123+45*(-6-(-7+8)+9+AB)$	$B+A+(9+8+7+6+5-4)^{\wedge}3-2*1$
3B93	06879	$-1234+56-7*-89A-B$	$-B-(-A9+8)-7+65*-4*(3-21)$
3B94	06880	$1*2*-34*(5+6-(-7+89+A-B))$	$B-A9+(87+6)*54-3+21$
3B95	06881	$1+2+3-4*-56*(-78+9A)+B$	$B-A-9*-8-7*65+4321$
3B96	06882	$-1*2*-3*(-45-6-(78-9A*B))$	$B-(-A9+8)-76*(5-4)*3*-21$
3B97	06883	$1-2345-6*7(-8-9A-B)$	$B-A9*(-8+7)-(-6-5)*(432-1)$
3B98	06884	$-1*2*(34-5*6*7+8+9A*B)$	$-B+A+98-7*(-654-32-1)$
3B99	06885	$-123+456*-7-89*-A*B$	$B+A+9-(8*(7-6^{\wedge}5/(4+3+2))+1)$
3B9A	06886	$12-(-3456-(7+89*A-B))$	$-B*(-A+987+6-543+2)*-1$
3B9B	06887	$-1+23*-4*-5*(6+7)-(-8+9)-AB$	$-B-(A98-765-4321)$
3BA0	06888	$-12*3*(4-(5+6+7+8)+A+B)$	$B-A-98*-7-(65+4)*3*-21$
3BA1	06889	$1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(5+6-(-7+8)*9)+A-B$	$B-A+9+8*7*-6+5+4321$
3BA2	06890	$123-(456+7*89*-A-B)$	$-BA+9-8*(-7-654)-321$
3BA3	06891	$-1-2+3456+7-89*-A+B$	$-BA9+8*765-43-21$
3BA4	06892	$1*-2+3456+7-89*-A+B$	$B+A+98-7*(-654-(32-1))$
3BA5	06893	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*-4^{\wedge}5*6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$-BA9-(-876+5-4321)$
3BA6	06894	$12+3456-(7-89*A-B)$	$B+A+9*-8*-76-54+321$
3BA7	06895	$-1-(-2-3456-7-(-89*-A+B))$	$-B+A9+8-7+65*-4*(3-21)$
3BA8	06896	$-1-234-5+6-7*8*(-9A-B)$	$-BA9-8*(-765+4)-(32+1)$
3BA9	06897	$-1-2345-6-7*8*-9A-B$	$B*(A9+8-(-7*6+5+4-321))$
3BAA	06898	$-1234-56+7*(-8+9A*B)$	$-B-(A9+8*7*-6-5)+4321$
3BAB	06899	$-12+3456-78+9*A*B$	$B+A*9-8*7*6*(54+3*-21)$
3BB0	06900	$123+4567-(-8-9*A*-B)$	$-BA98-7*-65*43-21$
3BB1	06901	$123-4+5*(67+89A)-B$	$B-(-A9+8)-7-65*4*(3-21)$
3BB2	06902	$12*(345-6-7-(8-9)*A+B)$	$B+A-9*8+7*654+321$
3BB3	06903	$-12-34+5+6*7*8*(9-A)*-B$	$-BA9+876+5+4321$
3BB4	06904	$-12-(-3456-789+A)-B$	$BA+9-8*7*(-6-54)-321$
3BB5	06905	$1+2+3+4*5*(6*7*8+9)+A-B$	$B-A9-8*(-7-654)-321$
3BB6	06906	$123-45+6*789+A*B$	$B+A-9*(-876+5+4321)$
3BB7	06907	$1-(2-3456-78)-9*A*-B$	$-B+A98-7*(6-543-2+1)$
3BB8	06908	$12+3456+7-89*-A+B$	$B*(-A+9)*(-8-(7-6+5+432)*1)$
3BB9	06909	$123+4-5*(-67-89A)-B$	$B-A98+765+4321$
3BBA	06910	$-1234-(-5+6+7*(-89A-B))$	$B-A98+7+6*54*(-3+21)$
3BBB	06911	$-1*(2-3456+78+9*-AB)$	$-B-A*-9*(-8+76)-5+4-321$
4000	06912	$-12+3+4+5*6*(7+8+9*A)-B$	$BA-(-9+8+7)+65*-4*(3-21)$
4001	06913	$1-2*3*-4*(56+7+89-A*-B)$	$B+A+9*(-8*7+(6*5-4/3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$
4002	06914	$-1+2+3456-78-9*-AB$	$-BA+9*(876-5+4-321)$
4003	06915	$-1-2-(-3456-789+A)-B$	$B+A-987*-6-5*4*-3*-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4004	06916	$1+2+3456-78-9^*-AB$	$B+A+(9^*(8+7)+6+5^4)*3^2+1$
4005	06917	$1-2+3456+789-(A+B)$	$-B+A-(9-8)-(-76^*-5-4321)$
4006	06918	$-1+2^*-3-(-4^45^*-6+7)/-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8^*765-43+2^*1$
4007	06919	$-1+2+3456+789-A-B$	$BA-98-7+6^*(-5+43)^*21$
4008	06920	$-1-(234+56)+7^*(89-A)^*B$	$B-A+9+8^*-7^*6-(-5-4321)$
4009	06921	$1-2345-6+78^*9A+B$	$-B+A^*-9^*(-87-(-65+43))^+2^*1$
400A	06922	$1234+5^*(678-9)+AB$	$-BA9-87^*6+5432-1$
400B	06923	$123-4-5^*(-67-89A)+B$	$-BA9+87^*-6+5432^*1$
4010	06924	$-12+3456-(-789-A)-B$	$-B-A+9+8^*(-7+654-32)^*1$
4011	06925	$-12+3456-(7+8^*(-9-AB))$	$BA9-8+76^*(54+3^*-2^*1)$
4012	06926	$-12-(-3456-789)-(A-B)$	$B+A-98+7^*(654-3^*-21)$
4013	06927	$123+4567+8^*-9A-B$	$-BA-(98+7^*-654)+321$
4014	06928	$-1+23^*-4^*-56-(78+9A-B)$	$BA-9+(8+7)^*(6-5)^*(-4+321)$
4015	06929	$1-2-34^*56^*-7+89^*-A^*B$	$-B+A^*(98+7^*-6+5+432+1)$
4016	06930	$12^*3^*(4-5+6)^*(7-(89-AB))$	$B^*(A+98)^*(-7-6+5^*-4+32^*1)$
4017	06931	$-1-(2345-6+78^*-9A-B)$	$-BA9+8^*(765-4)-(3+2-1)$
4018	06932	$12+3456+789-A-B$	$B+A+(9+8-7-6+5^4)^3/2-1$
4019	06933	$12-3+456^*-7+8^*9AB$	$-B-A+9-8+7^*654+321$
401A	06934	$12+34^*(56-(7+8)-9+AB)$	$-BA-98^*(76-(-5-4)-32)^*-1$
401B	06935	$-12+3456-7^*8+9^*AB$	$-B+A-(9+8)-(-7^*-654-321)$
4020	06936	$-1^*(2-(3456+789)-(A-B))$	$B+A^*98+76^*54+3+2^*1$
4021	06937	$1-2+3456+789+A-B$	$B-(A+9+8-(-7^*654+321))$
4022	06938	$123-45+(-67+8+9)^*-A^*B$	$B+A9-87^*6^*(54+3^*-21)$
4023	06939	$1-(2-(3456+789-A+B))$	$B+A-9+8-76^*5+4321$
4024	06940	$-1+2+3456+789^*(A+B)$	$B+A9+8^*(76-5^4-32^*1)$
4025	06941	$-1+2+3456+789-A+B$	$B^*(-A+9-(-8-(765-4))-321)$
4026	06942	$12-3-45-6^*(7+8-9^*AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6-5+4)^3/2^*1$
4027	06943	$1234+5^*678+9A-B$	$B+A98+7^*6^*54^*(3-2+1)$
4028	06944	$1^*-2^*(-3-45)^*(67-8-9)^*(-A+B)$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6+5)^4/3+2^1$
4029	06945	$1+2+3+45^*(6+7)^*8+9AB$	$BA-98+76^*-5+4321$
402A	06946	$-12+3456+789+A+B$	$-BA9-8^*-765-(4+3)^*(2+1)$
402B	06947	$-1-2-3-4+5+67^*-8^*(9-A)^*B$	$-B-A+987+654^*3^*2+1$
4030	06948	$-123-4-5-6^*(7-89-A)^*B$	$-B+A98+76^*-5^*-4^*3+2+1$
4031	06949	$123+4567+8^*-9A+B$	$-BA9+8^*765-(-4-3+21)$
4032	06950	$1+23+456^*-7+8^*9AB$	$-B+A9-(8^*-7-65^*-4^*(3-21))$
4033	06951	$1+2^*34+5^*-6^*(7-89-AB)$	$-B+A98^*7+65^*-43-(2+1)$
4034	06952	$12+3456+789+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8+(7^*6-5^4-3)^{(2+1)}$
4035	06953	$12+3456+789^*(A+B)$	$B-A-(9-8+7^*-654)+321$
4036	06954	$12-(-3456-789)-(A-B)$	$-BA9+8^*765-4-3^*(2+1)$
4037	06955	$1+2-(-345+6-789-A)^*B$	$-B-A98^*-7+65^*-43-(-2+1)$
4038	06956	$-1-2+3456-(-7-8+9A)^*-B$	$B+A^*(9-876)-543^*-21$
4039	06957	$-1-2+3456+789+A+B$	$-BA9+8^*(765-4)-3+21$
403A	06958	$123+4-5-6^*-789+A^*B$	$-B+A9-8^*(76+5)^*(4-(-3-2))^*-1$
403B	06959	$1-2+3456+789+A+B$	$-B+A98-7^*(-6-543)-21$
4040	06960	$1^*-2^*34^*(5+6+7-89^*(-A+B))$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^*(-6-5)^*(4+32)^*-1$
4041	06961	$-1+2+3456-(-789-A-B)$	$BA9+8^*(-76-(-543+21))$
4042	06962	$-1^*(2-3456-789-A-B)$	$B+A9-8+7^*-65+4321$
4043	06963	$1-234+56-7^*8^*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A987-65^*-4^*-32-1$
4044	06964	$-1-23^*-4^*56-7^*8-(9A-B)$	$-B-(-A987-65^*-4^*-32^*-1)$
4045	06965	$1234-5^*-678-(-9A-B)$	$B+A9-(-8+76+5+4)^*-3^*21$
4046	06966	$1^*-23^*(-45-(67+89-(-A-B)))$	$BA9-87^*(-65+43-21)$
4047	06967	$12-(-3456-7)+8^*(9+AB)$	$B+A+98-7^*65+4321$
4048	06968	$(-1-(2^3-4^45))^*-6/-7^*8+9+A-B$	$-BA9-8^*-765-4+3+2^*1$
4049	06969	$-1+23-(45-6+7+8-9)^*-AB$	$-BA9+8^*-765^*(-4+3)-2^*-1$
404A	06970	$1^*2+(-3+4^*(5^4+6+7^*8))/9+A-B$	$B-A^*(9-8+76-543+2)-1$
404B	06971	$123-4-(5-6^*789)+AB$	$-BA9+8^*765+4^*(3-2)^*1$
4050	06972	$-1-(2+3^*456+7^*-89A-B)$	$-B+A^*-9+8^*(-7+6^*-5)+4321$
4051	06973	$1+234-(-5-6)^*(-7^*-89-AB)$	$BA-(-9+8-7^*-65-4321)$
4052	06974	$12+3456-(-789-A)+B$	$-B^*(A-(-98-7)-(-6+543))+2^*-1$
4053	06975	$123+4+5^*(67+89A+B)$	$-BA9+8^*765+4-(-3-(2-1))$
4054	06976	$-12+3456-7-8-9^*-AB$	$-B-A+(987-6)^*5+4+3+21$
4055	06977	$12+3+4^*-56+7^*-8^*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-98+7)^*-6-5-4+321$
4056	06978	$-1-2-34^*5^*-6^*7+8-9AB$	$B+A9-(-8-7^*-65)+4321$
4057	06979	$12-34^*5^*-6^*7-(8+9AB)$	$BA-(98+7^*-654)+321$
4058	06980	$-1+2-345-6^*(-789-AB)$	$-B-A9^*8^*-7+65^*-4+3^*21$
4059	06981	$-1234-5^*67+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A^*(9-8)^*(7-(-65-432)-1)$
405A	06982	$1+2-345-6^*(-789-AB)$	$BA+9^*8^*(76-5-(-4-3-2-1))$
405B	06983	$-1-2^*3^*(45+6-789+A^*-B)$	$BA-9^*-8-7^*(-654-(32+1))$
4060	06984	$-12-34^*-5+6^*(-7-8+9A)^*B$	$-BA9+876^*(-5-4^*-3)+2+1$
4061	06985	$-1^*(2-3)^*(-456+7+89A)^*B$	$-B+A-987^*-6+54^*(3-21)$
4062	06986	$-12^*(34+56^*-7-(8+9-A)^*B)$	$-B+A9+87+(6+5)^*(432+1)$
4063	06987	$-1^*(23-(4-5+67))^*(8-(-9A-B))$	$B+A+9^*(8+(7-6-5)^4+3-2)^1$
4064	06988	$1+23+4^*-56+7^*-8^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A+987+654^*3^*-2^*-1$
4065	06989	$1-(2-3456)-(-7+8)-9^*-AB$	$-B+A^*(9-8+7+65+432+1)$
4066	06990	$-12+3456+7-8+9^*AB$	$BA-9+87-(-6-5)^*-432^*-1$
4067	06991	$-1-23^*4-5^*(6-7+8-9AB)$	$-BA9-8^*-765+4^*(3+2+1)$
4068	06992	$-1^*(-2-(3456-7-(8-9^*AB)))$	$B+A+9+8^*(-7-6^*5/4^3)^2/1$
4069	06993	$-1^*23^*(-45-(67+8+9-A^*-B))$	$-BA9-8^*-765+43-21$
406A	06994	$-1+23^*-45+67^*89+AB$	$BA+987^*6+543^*-2^*1$
406B	06995	$(-1-(-2-3^4+5)^*6)^*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7+6^*5)^4/3-2/1$
4070	06996	$1234+5^*(6+789-AB)$	$-B^*(A9-876-5^*-4+321)$
4071	06997	$-1+2^*345^*6+7-8+9^*AB$	$-B+A9+87-65^*4^*(3-21)$
4072	06998	$(-1+(-2-3+4^45^*6)/7)^*8-9+A-B$	$B-A^*-9^*(-8+76)+54-321$
4073	06999	$-1+234-(5-6^*789-(A-B))$	$-BA9-8^*(-765-4)-3+2+1$
4074	07000	$-12^*(-34+567-89A+B)$	$-BA9+8^*765-(4-32+1)$
4075	07001	$-1-(-234-(-5-6^*-789-A)-B)$	$-BA9-8^*-765-4+32^*1$
4076	07002	$1+234-5+6^*789^*(-A+B)$	$-B-A9^*-8^*7+6^*5^*(-4-3)-(-2-1)$
4077	07003	$-1-2+3456-7+8-9^*-AB$	$-BA9-8^*(-765-4)+3+2-1$
4078	07004	$12+3456-7-8+9^*AB$	$-B+A9+8^*(76+543)-2^*1$
4079	07005	$1-2+3456-(7-8+9^*-AB)$	$-BA9+8^*(765+4)-3^*2^*-1$
407A	07006	$-12-(-3456-7-8-9^*AB)$	$B-A-9-(87+6)^*-54+32^*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
407B	07007	$1 - (-2 - 3456 - 7) - (8 + 9 * - AB)$	$- B * (- A - 9 - (87 - 6 - (-54 - 321)))$
4080	07008	$- 1 - 23 * - 45 - 67 * 8 * - 9 + A * - B$	$- B - A * 9 * (8 - 76 + 5 - 4 + 3) - (2 - 1)$
4081	07009	$12 + 34 - (-56 - 7 + 8) * (9A - B)$	$- B + A * - 9 * (-8 + 7 - 6 + 5 - 43 - 21)$
4082	07010	$- 12 + 3 * - 45 * (6 + 7 - 8) * - 9 - AB$	$- BA9 - 8 * - 765 - (-4 - 32 - 1)$
4083	07011	$- 123 * (-4 - (-5 - 6) - (-78 + 9 + AB))$	$- BA + 9 + 8 * (-7 + 654 - 3 - 21)$
4084	07012	$1 + 2 - 34 * - 5 + 6 * 789 + AB$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 * 5 * 4 + 3 + 2) ^ \wedge 1$
4085	07013	$1 + 234 + 5 - (-6 * 789 + A) + B$	$- B + A98 - 7 + (-65 + 4) * - 3 * 21$
4086	07014	$- 12 * 3 * (45 - 6 - 78 - (-9 + AB))$	$BA + 9 + 8 * (76 + 543) - 21$
4087	07015	$(1 + 2 \wedge 3) \wedge 4 + 5 + (-6 + 7 * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9 - 8 * (-76 - 543 + 2 + 1)$
4088	07016	$(-1 + (-2 - 3 + 4 \wedge 5 * 6) / 7) * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$- BA - 98 - 76 - 5 + 4321$
4089	07017	$- 123 - 4 * 567 + 8 * - 9A * - B$	$BA - 9 + (-87 + 6) * 5 + 4321$
408A	07018	$12 + 3456 + 7 - 8 - 9 * - AB$	$B * (- A9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 543 - 21)$
408B	07019	$1 + 234 + 5 * (67 + 89A - B)$	$- BA9 + 8 * 765 + 43 + 2 - 1$
4090	07020	$12 + 3456 - (7 - 8) - 9 * - AB$	$B + A - 9 + 8 + 7 * (6 + 5 - 4 + 3) ^ \wedge (2 + 1)$
4091	07021	$1234 + 567 * 8 - 9AB$	$- BA9 + 8 * 765 - (-43 - (2 + 1))$
4092	07022	$- 1 - 2 + 34 - 5 * (6 - 7 - 8 - 9A) * B$	$BA - 9 - 8 * (-76 - 543) + 2 - 1$
4093	07023	$1 + 2 + 3456 + 7 + 8 + 9 * AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 - 5 * - 43 * 21$
4094	07024	$(-1 + 2 * 3 - 4 \wedge 5 * 6) / - 7 * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8 + 76 * 54 - 321$
4095	07025	$- 1 - 2 + 34 - (-567 + 8) * 9 - AB$	$B + A9 + 8 * (76 + 543) - (2 + 1)$
4096	07026	$1 * - 2 * - 3 * (-4 - 5 - 67 - (-89A + B))$	$- BA - (98 - (-76 + 5 + 4321))$
4097	07027	$- 1 - 2 * 3 * (-45 - 6 - 789 - (A - B))$	$- BA - 98 - 7 - 65 + 4321$
4098	07028	$- 12 - 3 + 4 + (-5 + 67) * (89 - A) + B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 + 4) ^ \wedge 3 - 2 / 1$
4099	07029	$- 1 * (23 - 456 * - 7 - 89 * A * B)$	$- B + A9 - 8 + 76 * - 5 + 4321$
409A	07030	$1 - (2 + 345) - 67 * (-89A + A) + B$	$- BA + 98 + 7 * - 6 * (5 + 43) * (-2 - 1)$
409B	07031	$1 - 2 - (-345 + 6 * - 789) - AB$	$- BA + 9 * (-87 + 654 - (3 + 21))$
40A0	07032	$1 - 23 - 4 + 56 * 78 - 9 * A * - B$	$BA9 + 8 + 76 * (54 - 3 - 2) + 1$
40A1	07033	$- 1 + 2 - (-3456 + 78 + 9A * - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 + 4) ^ \wedge 3 + 2 + 1$
40A2	07034	$- 1 * (-2 - (3456 - 78) - 9A * B)$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 * 6 + (5 + 4) ^ \wedge 3) + 2 * 1$
40A3	07035	$- 12 + 3456 + 789 - A * - B$	$- B - A - 9 + (-8 - 7) * (-654 + 321)$
40A4	07036	$- 12 - 3 * 4 - 56 * (7 + 8 + 9 - AB)$	$B - A + 98 - 76 * 5 + 4321$
40A5	07037	$- 1 + 2 * 3 * - 4 + 56 * (7 - 8) * (-9A + B)$	$- BA9 - 8 * (-765 - 4) + 32 * 1$
40A6	07038	$- 1 - 2 * 3 + 45 * - 6 + 7 * - 89 * - A + B$	$- BA - (9 + 87) - (65 - 4321)$
40A7	07039	$- 1 - 2 - 3 * - 4 + 5 * (-6 - 7 - 8 + 9AB)$	$B + A - 9 * 8 - 7 * (6 + 5 - 4 ^ \wedge (3 + 2)) - 1$
40A8	07040	$1 - 2345 - 6 * (7 + 8) * (9 - AB)$	$- B * - A * (-9 + 87 + 6 - 54 + 3 + 21)$
40A9	07041	$12 + 3456 - 7 * (8 + 9) * - A + B$	$- BA - 98 - (-7 + 65) + 4321$
40AA	07042	$- 12 * (345 - 6 - (789 - AB))$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 * 7) * - 6 * (5 + 4 + 3 ^ \wedge 2) + 1$
40AB	07043	$1 - 234 + 56 * 78 - 9A * - B$	$- BA9 + 8 * 765 - (-43 - 21)$
40B0	07044	$1 * 2 * 3 * (-4 - 56 + 789 + AB)$	$BA - 9 - (8 * (7 - 654) + 321)$
40B1	07045	$1234 - 5 * - 678 - (-9 - A) * B$	$- BA9 + 8 + 7 * (-6 + 5 + 43) * 21$
40B2	07046	$- 1 - (2 - 3456) + 789 - A * - B$	$B - A * - 9 - 8 - 7 * - 654 + 321$
40B3	07047	$1 * 23 * (-4 + 56 + 78 + 9A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 + (6 ^ \wedge 5 + 4) / (3 ^ \wedge 2 - 1)$
40B4	07048	$- 1 + 2 + 3456 - (78 + 9A) * - B$	$- B - A - (-98 - 7 * 654) + 321$
40B5	07049	$- 12 - (3 - 4 - (5 - 67 + 8) * (-9A + B))$	$- B - A9 - (87 + 65 - 4321)$
40B6	07050	$- 1 - 2 * - 3 * (4 + 56 + 789 - A) + B$	$- BA - 9 + 8 * 7 * (6 + 54) + 3 * (-2 - 1)$
40B7	07051	$- 1 - 2 * 3 * (-45 + 6) * (7 + 8 + 9 - A + B)$	$B * (A - 98 - (-7 + 6) + 543 - 21)$
40B8	07052	$1 - (-2 - 3456) + 789 - A * - B$	$BA + 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 * (-5 + 43) * - 21$
40B9	07053	$1 - 2 - 3456 - 78 * (-9 - AB)$	$- B + A * (-9 + 8 * 76) - (5 + 4 + 32 - 1)$
40BA	07054	$123 - 4 * - 56 + 7 * - 8 * - 9A + B$	$BA - 9 * 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 - 4 + 3 - 21)$
40BB	07055	$- 12 + 3 + 4 - 56 * 78 - 9 * - A * B$	$B - A9 + 8 * 7 * (6 + 54) - (32 - 1)$
4100	07056	$- 12 + 3456 + 789 + AB$	$- BA + 9 - 87 - (65 - 4321)$
4101	07057	$12 + 3456 + 7 + (8 - 9A) * - B$	$- B + A9 - (8 + 7 - 6) * 543 * (-2 + 1)$
4102	07058	$- 123 - 45 * 67 + 8 * 9AB$	$B - (-A - 9 - 8 * 7 * - 6) - 5 + 4321$
4103	07059	$1 \wedge 2 + 3 + (4 * - 5 + 6) * - 7 * 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A98 - 76 * (-54 + 3) + 2 * 1$
4104	07060	$1234 + 56 * - 7 * - 8 - 9A * - B$	$- B - A9 * - 8 * 7 - 65 - 43 - 21$
4105	07061	$12 + 3456 - (-78 - (9 + A)) * B$	$B + A + (9 / - 8 + 7 + 6 - 5) / 4 ^ \wedge (-3 - 2) * 1$
4106	07062	$1 * - 2 * 3 * (4 + 5 - (-6 - 78)) * (-9 + A) * - B$	$BA + 9 - 8 - 76 * 5 + 4321$
4107	07063	$- 1 - 2 * - 3 - 456 * 7 + 89 * A * B$	$- B + A9 - 8 + 7 * 654 + 321$
4108	07064	$- 12 + 3456 - 7 - (-89A + B)$	$B + A - (-987 - 6) * 5 - (4 - (-3 + 21))$
4109	07065	$- 1 + 2 - (3 - 4 + 5) - 6 * (-7 + 8 - 9 * AB)$	$B + A98 + 7 * 6 * - 5 * (-4 - 32 + 1)$
410A	07066	$(-1 - (2 + 3 - 4 \wedge 5) - 6) * 7 - 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5) / 4 ^ \wedge - 3 - 2 ^ \wedge - 1)$
410B	07067	$- 1 - 2 - (-3456 - (789 + AB))$	$B + A9 + 8 - 76 * 5 + 4321$
4110	07068	$1 * - 2 + 3456 + 789 + AB$	$- B + A + 98 - (7 * - 654 - 321)$
4111	07069	$12 - 3 - (4 - 56 * 78 - 9 * A * B)$	$BA9 + 8 * 7 * (-65 + 43) * - 2 * 1$
4112	07070	$12 * (345 - 67 - 8 + 9A - B)$	$- B - A9 + 8 * 7 * (6 + 54) - 3 + 2 + 1$
4113	07071	$- 1 + 2 - (-3456 - 789 - AB)$	$B - (A9 + 87) - (65 - 4321)$
4114	07072	$1 * (23 - 45 - 6) * (-78 - 9A - B)$	$B + A - 9 * - 8 * - 7 * (6 + 5 * - 4) - 3 * 2 + 1$
4115	07073	$1 + 2 + 3456 + 789 + AB$	$B * (A + 987 - (-6 + 543) - 2 + 1)$
4116	07074	$1 * 23 * (-45 - (-67 - 89 - AB))$	$- BA - 98 - 7 * 6 - (-5 - 4321)$
4117	07075	$- 1 - 2 + 3456 - 7 + 89A - B$	$B - A - 9 * (87 - 654 + 32 + 1)$
4118	07076	$1 * (-2 + 3) * (45 - (-6 - 7 + 8)) * (-9 + AB)$	$B + A + (9 + 8 - 7 - 6 * 5 - 4 ^ \wedge 3) ^ \wedge 2 - 1$
4119	07077	$1 - 2 - (-3456 + 7 - 89A + B)$	$B + A + (9 + 8 - 7 - 6 * 5 - 4 ^ \wedge 3) ^ \wedge 2 * 1$
411A	07078	$- 12 + 3456 + 7 + 89A - B$	$BA - 9 - (8 - 7 * 654 - 321)$
411B	07079	$- 1 + 2 + 3456 - 7 - (-89A + B)$	$- B + A * (-98 - 76 * 5 + 43 * 21)$
4120	07080	$1 * (2 + 3 - 4 + 5) * (-67 + 89A - B)$	$B + A - 9 + (8 - (-76 + 5)) * (43 + 21)$
4121	07081	$1 + 2 - (-3456 + 7) + 89A - B$	$BA9 - (8 + 7 * (6 - 543 - 2 - 1))$
4122	07082	$12 + 3456 + 7 * - 8 + 9A * B$	$B + A9 * 8 * 7 - 65 - 43 - 21$
4123	07083	$- 12 + 3456 + 78 - 9 * - AB$	$BA98 - 7654 - 321$
4124	07084	$12 - (-3456 - 789) + AB$	$- BA + 9 * - 8 * - 76 + 543 - 21$
4125	07085	$- 1 - 2 - 34 + 56 * (-7 + 8 + 9A - B)$	$B - (-A9 - (-8 - 7 * - 654 + 321))$
4126	07086	$- 12 + 3456 - 7 + 89A + B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * (5 * 4 + 3 - 2) ^ \wedge 1$
4127	07087	$1 + 2 * 345 * 6 - (-7 - 89A + B)$	$B - A9 + 8 * 7 * (6 + 54) - 3 + 2 * - 1$
4128	07088	$1 * 2 * (34 - (-5 * 67 - 8)) * (9 + A - B)$	$BA + 98 + 7 * - 65 + 4321$
4129	07089	$- 1 - 2 + 3456 - (-7 - (89A - B))$	$B + A + (9 - 8 * - 7 * (6 + 5 ^ \wedge 4)) / (3 + 2) - 1$
412A	07090	$- 123 + 45 * (-6 + 7) * (8 + 9A + B)$	$B - (A + 9 * 8 * - 76 - (-5 + 432) * 1)$
412B	07091	$1 - 2 - (-3456 - 7) - (-89A + B)$	$- B - A + (9 - 8 + 7) * (654 - 32 - 1)$
4130	07092	$12 - (-3456 + 7 - 89A + B)$	$BA - 9 + (-8 + 76) * - 5 + 4321$
4131	07093	$- 1 + 2 + 3456 - (-7 - 89A) - B$	$- BA - 98 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4321$
4132	07094	$1 * 2 + 3456 + 7 + 89A - B$	$B - A9 - 8 + (-76 - 5) * (-43 - 21)$
4133	07095	$- 12 + 3456 - 7 - 8 + 9A * B$	$B * A9 * (-8 + 7 * - 6 - 5 * 4 + 3 * 21)$
4134	07096	$1 - 23 * - 4 * 56 - 7 + 89 - AB$	$B + A - (-98 * (76 + 5 + 4 - 32) + 1)$
4135	07097	$- 1 - 2 + 3456 - 7 + 89A + B$	$B + A - 9 + (-8 * (-7 - 6) + 5) * (4 ^ \wedge 3 + 2 - 1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4136	07098	$1+2*3-(-4-56)*(78+9)-(-A-B)$	$-B-A+9*(8*7+6+(5+4)^3(2-1))$
4137	07099	$1-2-(-3456-(-7+89A))+B$	$-B-A+9-8*7*(-6+5-4^3*2)-1$
4138	07100	$-12+3456+7+89A+B$	$-BA*(-98-(-7-(-6+54)))-(-3-2*-1))$
4139	07101	$-1-2-345+6*(-7+89A)+B$	$B+A9-(-8+7*-654-321)$
413A	07102	$1+2+3-4*-56-7*8*(9-AB)$	$BA+98*(7+65-(-4+3+21))$
413B	07103	$1+2+3456-7+89A+B$	$-BA-98-7-(6-5-4321)$
4140	07104	$-1-(-2+3)-(4-5*(-6-7+8+9AB))$	$-BA-9-87-6-5+4321$
4141	07105	$1+2*-3*(-4-56-789+A-B)$	$-BA-98-7+6-5+4321$
4142	07106	$12+3456+7-(-89A+B)$	$-B*(-A98+765-(4+3)*21)$
4143	07107	$12-3+4*56-7*-8*(-9+AB)$	$-BA-98-(-7+6)-5+4321$
4144	07108	$1+2-3+(4^5-6)*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA9-8-76*-5*4*3-(-2-1)$
4145	07109	$-1-2-345+(67-8)*(9A-B)$	$BA+987-654*3*-2*1$
4146	07110	$1+23*4*56-(-7-89+AB)$	$BA+987-654*-3*2+1$
4147	07111	$-1-2+3456+7+89A+B$	$-B+A9+87*6*5*-43*21$
4148	07112	$1+23*4*-5+6*(7+89A)-B$	$BA-(-9-8-7*654)+321$
4149	07113	$1-(2-(3456+7+89A+B))$	$-B+A-987*-6-5-43*21$
414A	07114	$12-(-3456+7-89A)+B$	$-BA-9-87-(6-(5+4321))$
414B	07115	$-1+2+3456+7+89A+B$	$-BA-9-(8+76+5-4321)$
4150	07116	$1+23*4*56+7-8+9-(A+B)$	$-BA-9-87+6-5+4321$
4151	07117	$1-(-2-3456-7)+89A+B$	$-BA-98+7-(6-5-4321)$
4152	07118	$12-3*456+7*(-8+9A*B)$	$B-A9-87+6*-5+4321$
4153	07119	$-12+3*4-567+8*9*A*B$	$-BA-98+7+6-5+4321$
4154	07120	$-123-4-56-7*89*-A+B$	$-BA9+8*765+43*(2+1)$
4155	07121	$-123-45+6-7*-89*A-B$	$-B-(A+9)-(8+7*-6*-5-4321)$
4156	07122	$1+234+5+6*789+A*B$	$-BA+9-87-(6-(-5+4321))$
4157	07123	$12-(-3456+7)-(8+9A*-B)$	$-BA9-8*765-4*(-32-1)$
4158	07124	$-1+234+56*(78+9)+AB$	$BA9-8*7+65*(-4-3*-21)$
4159	07125	$1-2*(-3+456*-7)+(8+9)*-A*B$	$BA+9*(-8+7+6+5+43)-2+1$
415A	07126	$1-(-2-3456)+7-(8-9A*B)$	$-BA-9-87+6+5+4321$
415B	07127	$-1*(-2-3456+7-8+9A*B)$	$-B-A9-87+6-5+4321$
4160	07128	$12+3456+7-(-89A-B)$	$B+A98-7+654*3*-2*-1$
4161	07129	$-1+2+3*4*56*(-78-9+A*B)$	$-BA-98-(-7-6-5-4321)$
4162	07130	$-1-234-5-6*(-789-AB)$	$BA9-8+76*5*4*3+21$
4163	07131	$-1+234-5+6*789+AB$	$-BA-(9-8)-(76+5)+4321$
4164	07132	$1+2-(-3-4^5+6)*7-8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9-87-6-(-5-4321)$
4165	07133	$1+234-5+6*789+AB$	$-BA+9-8-76-(5-4321)$
4166	07134	$1*(-2-(-3+4))*(-5-678-9AB)$	$-BA-98-(-7*6*5-4321)$
4167	07135	$123+4-5*6*(-78-(9+AB))$	$B-A98-765*4*(-3+2-1)$
4168	07136	$-1-2-(-3456-7)+8+9A*B$	$-B-A9-(8+76-5)+4321$
4169	07137	$1+2*-3*4+5*(6-(-7-(-8+9AB)))$	$-B-(A+98)-(-76+5-4321)$
416A	07138	$-12-3-4-5-6*(-7-8-9*AB)$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7*-6*-5-4*3)*2+1$
416B	07139	$1234+5-6*78*-9-A*-B$	$-B*(A-987-6+543-21)$
4170	07140	$-1+2+3456-(-7-8)-9A*-B$	$-BA-(9+8)-(-7+65-4321)$
4171	07141	$-1-((-2+3)*-4^5+6)*7+8+9+A-B$	$-BA-9+8-76-(-5-4321)$
4172	07142	$1-234+5+6*(789+AB)$	$-B-(A9-8+76+5)+4321$
4173	07143	$12-3*(4+56)+7*-89*-A-B$	$-BA-(-9+8+76)-(-5-4321)$
4174	07144	$1-23*4*-56-78+9A-B$	$-BA+9-8-(7+65-4321)$
4175	07145	$1+2-(-345-6*789)-A-B$	$BA9+8*(-76+543-2*1)$
4176	07146	$1-2*-3*4-567+8*9*A*B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6+5+4^3(3*2/1)$
4177	07147	$-12+3456-(78-9AB)$	$BA9-8-(7*(-6-543))-2-1$
4178	07148	$-12+345+6*789+A-B$	$-B-A-98-7-65+4321$
4179	07149	$12+3456-(7-8-9A)*B$	$-BA+9+8-76-5+4321$
417A	07150	$1*(23-(4+567-8)+9A)*-B$	$-B*(A9-87)*(-6+5+4-3-21)$
417B	07151	$-123-4-(-5-6)-7*(89-A)*-B$	$-B-A9*8*-7-6-5-43*(2-1)$
4180	07152	$1+23+4*(567-8-9*A*-B)$	$-B-A9+8-76+5+4321$
4181	07153	$123-45*-6-7*8*(-9+A*-B)$	$-B-(A9-8+7+65)+4321$
4182	07154	$-1+2*345*6-(78-9AB)$	$B+A+9-8*(-7-6)*(5+4^3-2^8-1)$
4183	07155	$1*23*-45*(67-(89-A-B))$	$-B-A+9+8-7*6*5+4321$
4184	07156	$1*-2+3+45*(-6-7+8+9+AB)$	$-BA-9-(-8-(-7-65))+4321$
4185	07157	$-1+2*(3-4+5)^6*7/8-9+A-B$	$-B+A-98-(76-(-5+4321))$
4186	07158	$-1-2+3456-78+9AB$	$B-A9-(8+76-5)+4321$
4187	07159	$1*-2-(-3456-(78+9AB))$	$B-(A+98+76)-(5-4321)$
4188	07160	$1-(2-3456)-78+9AB$	$-BA-(-9-8+7)-65+4321$
4189	07161	$-1-234+5*(67-8+9AB)$	$-B*(-A9-(-8-76))*(-5+43-21)$
418A	07162	$-1+2+3456-78+9AB$	$-B-A-98+7-65+4321$
418B	07163	$-1*(-2-34+567-8*-9*A*-B)$	$-BA+9-87+6*5+4321$
4190	07164	$1+2-(-3456+78)+9AB$	$B-A9+8-(76-(-5+4321))$
4191	07165	$-1+2+345-(-6*789+A)+B$	$BA9-8-7*6*-5*(43-21)$
4192	07166	$-1234-5*6*7-8*-9*A*B$	$-BA-9+87*65-432*1$
4193	07167	$1+2+345-6*-789-(A-B)$	$BA-9*-8-7*-654+321$
4194	07168	$12*(-345-6+789-A*B)$	$-B+A-(98+7)-65+4321$
4195	07169	$1-2-(3-4)-(-5+6*(-7-8-9*AB))$	$B-A-98-76+5+4321$
4196	07170	$-1-234-56*-78+9AB$	$B-A-98-7-65+4321$
4197	07171	$-1*(234-56*78-9AB)$	$-B+A9*-8*-7-(65-(-4+32))-1$
4198	07172	$1-234+56*78+9AB$	$-B*(-A9+8+7-(-65+432+1))$
4199	07173	$(1+2^3(3-4+5+6))^7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A-98-76*(-5-43-21)$
419A	07174	$-1234+56*(-7+8)*(9+AB)$	$B-A9+8-76+5+4321$
419B	07175	$1+2*(3+4)+5*(6+7-8+9AB)$	$B-A9-(-8+7)-(-65-4321)$
41A0	07176	$-1+23+45*6+7*8*(-9+AB)$	$BA9+8*(-76-(-543-2))-1$
41A1	07177	$-1-2+3456-7*-8-9A*-B$	$BA+98-76*5+4321$
41A2	07178	$12+345+6*789-A+B$	$BA9-87+654*-3*-2*1$
41A3	07179	$1-2+3456-7*-8-9A*-B$	$B+A-98-76-5+4321$
41A4	07180	$12-345-6*(-7-89A)-B$	$-B+A9-8+(7-65)*(43*-2+1)$
41A5	07181	$-1+2+3456+7*8-9A*-B$	$B-A-9-(87+65-4321)$
41A6	07182	$1-2*3*(4-56-789)+AB$	$-B+A*98-76*(-54-3)+2+1$
41A7	07183	$-12+3456-7*8+9AB$	$B*(A-98+7+6+543-21)$
41A8	07184	$-12+34-(56-7*8*(9A+B))$	$B-(A+98-7-(-65+4321))$
41A9	07185	$-123+4+5-6*7*(8+9-A*B)$	$BA+98*-7-65*-43*2+1$
41AA	07186	$-1+2-(3+45)-(-6-7*-8*(-9A-B))$	$BA9+8-76*(-54+3)-21$
41AB	07187	$1-2*3+(4^5+6)*7-(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*8*(-76-5-4)-32*-1$
41B0	07188	$-1-234+5-6*(7-89A+B)$	$-B-A9*-8*7+6-5-4+3-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
41B1	07189	$1234-56*7*-8+9AB$	$B-A9+8+7-65+4321$
41B2	07190	$1-2*34*5-6*(7-89A)+B$	$-B-A9+8-7*6-(5-4321)$
41B3	07191	$(1-2)^3+(4^5+6)*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA-987+6*54*(-3+21)$
41B4	07192	$1*(-23-4)*(5+6-(7+89+AB))$	$-BA-(9+87-65)+4321$
41B5	07193	$-123-(-4-(5-6)-7*-89*-A)+B$	$BA9-8-76*(-5+43)+2*-1$
41B6	07194	$12+3456+7*8+9A*B$	$B+A-9*8+7*(6+5+4^(3+2))^A1$
41B7	07195	$1+2*-345-67*-89-AB$	$-BA-(98-7-65)+4321$
41B8	07196	$1-2-(-3456+7*8-9AB)$	$-BA-98-(-76+5)+4321$
41B9	07197	$-12-34-56*-78+9*AB$	$-B+A+9-(87+65)+4321$
41BA	07198	$-1+2+3456-7*8+9AB$	$-B-(A9+8-(7+6*-5+4321))$
41BB	07199	$1-2-34-5*(-6-7-8-9AB)$	$B-(A-9-(-87-65)-4321)$
4200	07200	$1+2+3456-7*8+9AB$	$B-(A9+87*-65)-(432-1)$
4201	07201	$-1-23+45*-67+8*9AB$	$B-(-A+9)-(87-(-65+4321))$
4202	07202	$-12+3456+78-9A*-B$	$-BA-9-(8+7)-(6-5-4321)$
4203	07203	$-1-23-4+5+6+7*-8*(-9A-B)$	$-B-A9-87+65+4321$
4204	07204	$12-3*4+567*(8-9+A)+B$	$B-(-A+98-7)-(65-4321)$
4205	07205	$-1-(2345-6+789*-A)+B$	$-B*(A9-876-(-5+4-321))$
4206	07206	$-1+23-(-4-56)*(78+9)+A*B$	$-BA-98+76+5+4321$
4207	07207	$-12-34+56*(7+89)-AB$	$B-A-(98+7*6)-(-5-4321)$
4208	07208	$1*(-2+3)*-45*(67-89-A*B)$	$-BA-9+8-7-(6+5-4321)$
4209	07209	$1^2+3+(4^5+6)*7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A*-98*7-(65+4-3)+21$
420A	07210	$-12*(345+6+7+8+9)*(A-B)$	$-BA+9-8-7-6-5+4321$
420B	07211	$12+3456+7*-8+9AB$	$BA+98+7*65+4321$
4210	07212	$-12-3-45*67+8*9AB$	$B-A9+8+7*-6-5+4321$
4211	07213	$-1-2+3456+78+9A*B$	$-B-A9*8*7*(6-5+4-3-2-1)$
4212	07214	$12-34*-5*(-67-(-8-9A+B))$	$-B-A9+8+7+6*-5+4321$
4213	07215	$12+3-456-7*8*(-9-AB)$	$-B-(-A+98+7)+6*-5+4321$
4214	07216	$1+23-(4*567+8*-9A*B)$	$-BA-9-8-(-7+6)-(-5-4321)$
4215	07217	$-1+23*-4*-5-6*789*(A-B)$	$-B+A9*-8*-7-6*5-4+32*1$
4216	07218	$-1*(-2-3456-78+9A*-B)$	$-BA-(9+8-7-(6-5)-4321)$
4217	07219	$1-(2-34+5*(6-7-8-9AB))$	$-B+A-9*-8*76-5*4*(-32+1)$
4218	07220	$(-1+2^3)*4^5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$-BA-9+8-7+6-5+4321$
4219	07221	$1-23-4-56*-78+9*AB$	$-B-A98*-7+6*(5-432-1)$
421A	07222	$-1+2*-3+45*-67-8*-9AB$	$-BA-(-9-(-8-7-(-6+5)+4321))$
421B	07223	$-1-2-3-45*67-8*-9AB$	$BA-9*-8*(-7*-6+5+43)+21$
4220	07224	$1*2*3*(4-(56-7)-(-89A+B))$	$-BA-(-9+8)+7-6-(5-4321)$
4221	07225	$-123+4+56*-7*(-8-9-A+B)$	$BA9+8*-7-65+4*3*2*-1$
4222	07226	$1+23*4*(-56+7+8+9A)-B$	$-B+A-9-8*7-65+4321$
4223	07227	$-123+45+6-7*89*-A-B$	$-B*(-A-98-(-7+65-(-4-321)))$
4224	07228	$1-23*(-4+56)+7*89A+B$	$-BA-9-8-(-7-6-5-4321)$
4225	07229	$-12-(345-6*(7+89A+B))$	$-B-(A9+8-7-6+5-4321)$
4226	07230	$12-(-3456-78)+9A*B$	$-B-A-(9+8)*7-(-6+5-4321)$
4227	07231	$-12-34-5*6+7*(89-A)*B$	$-B-(A9-8)-(7-6+5)+4321$
4228	07232	$1-23*4*-56+78+(-9+A)*B$	$-BA-(9-8-7)-6-(-5-4321)$
4229	07233	$-1-23+456+7*8*9A+B$	$-BA-9-(8+7)-6*-5+4321$
422A	07234	$-12+3-4-56+7*(89-A)*B$	$-BA-9+8-(-7-(6-5))+4321$
422B	07235	$1+2-(-3-45*-67)+8*9AB$	$B+A9*-8*-7*(65-43-21)$
4230	07236	$1*-2+3456-(7+8)+9AB$	$-B-A-(9+8+76+5-4321)$
4231	07237	$1-2+3456-7-8+9AB$	$B+A-(98+7-6*5)+4321$
4232	07238	$-12+3456-(-7+8-9AB)$	$B*(A98-7-654-(-32+1))$
4233	07239	$-1+2+3456-7-8+9AB$	$B-A9-(8-7-(-6-5)-4321)$
4234	07240	$-12+3456-7+8+9AB$	$-BA-(-9-8-7)-(6+5)+4321$
4235	07241	$1-(-2-3456)-7-(8-9AB)$	$-B-A9+8-7+6+5+4321$
4236	07242	$-1*2*3*(45+6-(7+89A)+B)$	$-B+A*-9-87+65+4321$
4237	07243	$1*-234+567*8+9*AB$	$-B-A9+8-(-7+6)+5+4321$
4238	07244	$-1+234*-5+6-7*-89A-B$	$-B+A-(98-(-7-6-(-5-4321)))$
4239	07245	$-1*(-2-3)*(-4-56-(-78-9AB))$	$-B+A-9-87-6-5+4321$
423A	07246	$-12+3*-4*(5-6-7*89+AB)$	$B-A-98-7-6+5+4321$
423B	07247	$12-34-56+7*-89*-A-B$	$B+A+9*-8*76-(-543+21)$
4240	07248	$-1-2-3*45+6*(-7*-8-9*-AB)$	$-BA+98-76-(5-4321)$
4241	07249	$1-2+3-(4+56*-78+9*AB)$	$B-A9-8-7-6+5+4321$
4242	07250	$-1+2-3*-4*-5-6+7*(-89+A)*-B$	$B-A-98+7-6-5+4321$
4243	07251	$1-(2-3456)-(-7+8-9AB)$	$B-A9-8+7+6-5+4321$
4244	07252	$12+3456-7-(8-9AB)$	$-BA+9-(-8-(7+6)+5)+4321$
4245	07253	$1-2-(-3456+7)+8+9AB$	$B-(A9-8)-(-7-(6-5)-4321)$
4246	07254	$-12+3456+7+8+9AB$	$-B-A-(-9+8+76+5)+4321$
4247	07255	$-1+2+3456-7+8+9AB$	$-B-A+9-87+6-5+4321$
4248	07256	$12+3+456+7*8*9A-B$	$B+A-98-7-6-5+4321$
4249	07257	$1-(-2-3456+7)-(-8-9AB)$	$-BA+9+8*-7+65+4321$
424A	07258	$-1-23*-4*(5-67)+89AB$	$-BA-98-76+5+4321$
424B	07259	$1+23*4*56-7-(-8-9A)+B$	$B-(A+9-(-87+6-5)-4321)$
4250	07260	$-1*-2*-3*(-4+5+67+8+9A*-B)$	$B+A9*8-76*-54+321$
4251	07261	$-1*(23-45+67)*(-8-9A-B)$	$-B-A-9-8-(-7+65)+4321$
4252	07262	$-1-2*-3-4-(-56*(7+89)+AB)$	$-BA+9+87-65+4321$
4253	07263	$1+2*345*6+7+8+9AB$	$B-(A9-8+7)-(-6-(5+4321))$
4254	07264	$12-3-(-4+56)+7*(-89+A)*-B$	$-BA+98-76*(-5-43-21)$
4255	07265	$-1-(2-3456)-(-7-8-9AB)$	$-B-A+9-8-7-6+5+4321$
4256	07266	$12+3456+7-(-8-9AB)$	$B+A+9+8*-7-65+4321$
4257	07267	$1-2+3456+7+8+9AB$	$-BA+9+8-(7-(-6*-5+4321))$
4258	07268	$12+3456-7+8+9AB$	$B-(A+9+8+76-5-4321)$
4259	07269	$-1+2+3456-(-7-(8+9AB))$	$B-A-9-87+6+5+4321$
425A	07270	$-123-45+67*(89-A)-B$	$-B+A-98+7+6+5+4321$
425B	07271	$1+2+3456-(-7-8)+9AB$	$-B-A9*-8*7-6-(-54+3-2)+1$
4260	07272	$1+2*3*-4*56-7*(89+A)*-B$	$-BA9-8-7-6*-5*4*-3*-21$
4261	07273	$-123+4*-5-6*(-789-AB)$	$-BA+98+7-65+4321$
4262	07274	$-1+2+345-(-6*789+A*-B)$	$-B-A-9-(-8+76+5-4321)$
4263	07275	$-12+34-(-56-7*(89-A)*B)$	$-B+A+9-87+6-5+4321$
4264	07276	$1*(-23+4-5-6)*(-78-(-9+AB))$	$B-A-(-9+8+76)-(-5-4321)$
4265	07277	$-12+34*(-5+67+89)+AB$	$B-A9+8-(-7-6-(5+4321))$
4266	07278	$-1*-2*(3-4-(-56+78))*(-9-AB))$	$B-(-A+9+8+76+5-4321)$
4267	07279	$-12+34*-56+7*(-8+9AB)$	$-B-(A+98-7*6)+5+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4268	07280	$-12*34*(-5-(-67+8)-(9*A-B))$	$-BA-9-8-7-(-65-4321)$
4269	07281	$-1+23+4-56*78+9*AB$	$BA9-8+7-(654*-3*2-1)$
426A	07282	$12+3456-(-7-8)+9AB$	$-B*(A-(98+76)-(-5+4)-321)$
426B	07283	$12+34*(56+7*(8+9))-AB$	$-BA-9*87+654*-3*(-2-1)$
4270	07284	$(-1+2)*3+(4^5+6)*7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9+8+76-5-4321)$
4271	07285	$-1*(2+3)*(-4+56-78-9AB)$	$-B+A-(-9+8+7+65-4321)$
4272	07286	$12+34*(5+6)-7*-8*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A-(9+87)-6*-5+4321$
4273	07287	$12+345-6*-789+A*B$	$B+A+9-87-(-6-5)+4321$
4274	07288	$12-3-(-4+56)+7*89*A-B$	$-B-A-9-87*-65-432+1$
4275	07289	$1/2*3/4*5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$B+A98-76*-54+32*-1$
4276	07290	$1-(2345-6)+78*(-9+AB)$	$B-A9-8-7*-6+5+4321$
4277	07291	$-1-2+345+6*789+AB$	$-BA-9+87-6*5+4321$
4278	07292	$1+2+3-4+56-7*8*(-9A-B)$	$B-A+9+8-76-5+4321$
4279	07293	$-1234-(56+7)+8*-9*-AB$	$-B*(-A+98-(76-(5-4)))*(-32-1)$
427A	07294	$12+34*(-5-(6-78+9))+A*B$	$-BA-9-8+7-(-65-4321)$
427B	07295	$-1+2-(-345+6*-789-AB)$	$B+A+9-87-6+5+4321$
4280	07296	$12-3-456+7-8*9*-A*B$	$-BA-9+8-7+65+4321$
4281	07297	$-1-2*-3*(4-(5-6))*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A*-9-8+7*6-5+4321$
4282	07298	$-1-23*-45*6+(-7-(-8+9A))*B$	$-BA+9-8-7+65+4321$
4283	07299	$-1+23*45-(6*(7+89))*-A+B$	$B-(-A98-76*54+3)-21$
4284	07300	$1+(-2-3)*-4*-5*(6-7-8*9)+A-B$	$-B+A+9+8-76-(-5-4321)$
4285	07301	$1-(2+3*4-5+6+7*(-89+A))*B$	$-B+A+9-(-8+7+65)+4321$
4286	07302	$-1234+5-67+8*9*AB$	$-B-(A-9+8)-(-7*6+5-4321)$
4287	07303	$12+345+6*(789-(-A-B))$	$B-A-(-9-8+7)-65+4321$
4288	07304	$-123+4567-89-AB$	$B*(A-9)*(87*6+5-(-4-32+1))$
4289	07305	$-1*(2+3)*(45-67-8-9AB)$	$B+A-9+8-7-65+4321$
428A	07306	$-1-2-(-3456-7*8-9AB)$	$-B-A9-8+76-5+4321$
428B	07307	$-1-2-34-(-5-6-7*89*A+B)$	$-B+A9-87-65+4321$
4290	07308	$12+345+6*789+AB$	$B-A-9-(87*-65-(-432-1))$
4291	07309	$1-2-34+5+6+7*89*A-B$	$-BA-(-9-87-6*-5-4321)$
4292	07310	$1-2+345-6+7*-8*(9-AB)$	$BA-98-76-(-5-4321)$
4293	07311	$1*2+(3^4+5)*(6+7+8*9)+A-B$	$BA-98-7-65+4321$
4294	07312	$-1+23-4+56-7*8*(-9A-B)$	$-BA+9-(8-7-(65+4321))$
4295	07313	$12-(3+45+6)-7*89*-A+B$	$B-A-9-8-7+65+4321$
4296	07314	$1*-2*3*(45-(6+7+89A-B))$	$-BA+9-(-8+7-65)+4321$
4297	07315	$-123-4-5*(-67+8-9AB)$	$-B*(-A-(-9-8))*(76+5)*(-4-3*(-2+1))$
4298	07316	$-12+3-4+5*-6+7*89*A+B$	$-B-A9*-8*7+65+43-21$
4299	07317	$-123+4*56-7*8*(-9A-B)$	$-B-A-(98-76+5-4321)$
429A	07318	$-1-(-23+45-6+7*-89*A+B)$	$-BA-98-7*(6+5)+4321$
429B	07319	$1*2*3*4*(5*6+7)*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-(9-(8+7))-(-65-4321)$
42A0	07320	$-1+23-45-67*(8-9*A-B)$	$-BA-9+87-6+5+4321$
42A1	07321	$-12+34-56-7*89*-A+B$	$-BA-9+8+76-(-5-4321)$
42A2	07322	$12*(-34-(-567+89)-AB)$	$-BA-9-(-87-6+5)+4321$
42A3	07323	$12+3456+7*8+9AB$	$-BA+9-8+76-(-5-4321)$
42A4	07324	$-12+34-5*-6-78*(9*-A+B)$	$B-A-(98+7-(65+4321))$
42A5	07325	$-123+4567-89+A*-B$	$BA-98-(-7+65-4321)$
42A6	07326	$123-45*(6-(-7+8-(-9-AB)))$	$B-A*(-9+87)*6-(-54-3)*21$
42A7	07327	$12+34-56-7*89*-A-B$	$-B-A-98+76-(-5-4321)$
42A8	07328	$1-2+(-34-56+78+89)*-A-B$	$-B+A9+87*(6+54)-(-3-2-1)$
42A9	07329	$1*(-234+5+67-89)*(A-B)$	$B-(-A9+87)-65+4321$
42AA	07330	$(1+2*3+4^5+6)*7+8*9+A-B$	$-B+A-9+8-7*6+5+4321$
42AB	07331	$-12+3456+78+9AB$	$-B-A9+87-6+5+4321$
42B0	07332	$-123+4-56*78+9AB$	$-B-(A9-8)-(-76-5-4321)$
42B1	07333	$12-3-4-(-5+67)*(8-(9A-B))$	$-B-(-A+9*8-7*6+5-4321)$
42B2	07334	$12+3-4-(5-6*(78-9A))*-B$	$-BA9-87-6*(-54+3)*21$
42B3	07335	$-1-23-45*67-89*-A*B$	$B-A-(9*8-7+6*-5-4321)$
42B4	07336	$1*-2*(-34+5*-6-7+89)*-AB$	$B+A-9-8-(7+6*5)+4321$
42B5	07337	$-1-2*3+4-5+6-7*-89*A-B$	$-B+A-98+76-5+4321$
42B6	07338	$-1-2*345*-6-(-78-9AB)$	$B-A9-8+76+5+4321$
42B7	07339	$-12-(34+56*(7-89)+A)+B$	$-BA+9+8+76+5+4321$
42B8	07340	$-1-2+(-3*-4*-5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$BA+9-(87+65-4321)$
42B9	07341	$12-(3-4)+56*(7-(-89A)-B)$	$-B-A+9-8-(7+6-5)+4321$
42BA	07342	$-1-2+3456+78+9AB$	$-B-A*(98+7)*-6-54+32-1$
42BB	07343	$1*-2+3456-(-78-9AB)$	$-B-(A9-87)-(-6-5-4321)$
4300	07344	$1-2+3456+78+9AB$	$B-(A9-8)-(-76+5)+4321$
4301	07345	$-12-3+45-6-7*(-89+A)*B$	$-BA9-(-8+76-5*-4*-321)$
4302	07346	$-123+45-6*(-789-AB)$	$B+A+9-87*-65-432-1$
4303	07347	$-1*(-2-(3456+78)-9AB)$	$-BA+98-7+6+5+4321$
4304	07348	$1+2-(-3456-78-9AB)$	$B+A*9+87*(6+54)+32-1$
4305	07349	$-12-3-4-56*-78-9A*-B$	$-BA+98-(-7-(-6+5))+4321$
4306	07350	$-123-4+5*-67+8*9*A*B$	$-BA+98-7*(-6+5)+4321$
4307	07351	$1-234+5-6*(-7-89A)+B$	$-BA+98+7+6-5+4321$
4308	07352	$-1+23*(-4-5)-6*(-7-(89A-B))$	$-BA+9-(87*6-5-43*21)$
4309	07353	$-123*(45-(-6+78+9))-(-A+B)$	$B-(A9-(87-6+5+4321))$
430A	07354	$-1-(2-3)+4567-(-8-9)*(-A-B)$	$B-A9-87*(-6+5)+4321$
430B	07355	$-1*(2+3)*(-45-6+7+8-9AB)$	$B-A9-(-87-6+5-4321)$
4310	07356	$-123+4+56*(7+89)+AB$	$-B+A+9+8*7-65+4321$
4311	07357	$-12-3+4-56*-78+9A*B$	$-B-A*98*-7-6-543+21$
4312	07358	$-1234-5-6-7+8*9*AB$	$-B+A-9*-8*7+(-6-5-4)*-321$
4313	07359	$12-(-3456-78)+9AB$	$-B+A-9+8-7-6+5+4321$
4314	07360	$1*(-23+4)*(-5-67-89-AB)$	$-B-(A-(-9+8*-7+65+4321))$
4315	07361	$1-234-(-5-678)*(9+A-B)$	$-B-A*(-9+8-7)-65+4321$
4316	07362	$1+2-(-3+4-5)-(-6+7*-89*A-B)$	$-BA-(98-765*(4+3)-21)$
4317	07363	$-1*(2-34-5+6)*(78+9A-B)$	$B-A-9+8-(7-6)-5+4321$
4318	07364	$-12*(3-456+7+89-A+B)$	$B+A98+76*54-(-32+1)$
4319	07365	$1-(-2-34)-5-((-6-7*8)*9A-B)$	$-B-A-9-(-87+65)+4321$
431A	07366	$1+2-(3+4+56*-78)-9A*-B$	$-B+A*98-76*-54+321$
431B	07367	$-1+23+4+56*(78+9A)+B$	$B+A-9-8-7+6-5+4321$
4320	07368	$1-2-(-3+4)-(-56*-78-9A*B)$	$-B-A-9-8+7+6*5+4321$
4321	07369	$-123-4567+89AB$	$B+A-98+76-(-5-4321)$
4322	07370	$-1234-5+6-7+8*-9*-AB$	$B*(A98-76-543-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4323	07371	$-1*23*(4+5-67+8*-9-AB)$	$-B-A+9+8-(-7+6)+5+4321$
4324	07372	$1-2-34-56*(-7-89)-(-A-B)$	$B-(A+9)-(-8+7)*6+5+4321$
4325	07373	$-12-34+56-(-7*-89*-A-B)$	$-B+A9-87-6-(5-4321)$
4326	07374	$1*-23-4+56+7*89*A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7-6+5^4)*3/-2*1$
4327	07375	$-12+3+4+567*8-9*-A*B$	$-B+A-9-(-8-7-6-(-5+4321))$
4328	07376	$(-1-2-3*4*(-5-6)*7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA-98+7*-6*5*(4-32-1)$
4329	07377	$123+4+567*(8-9+A)+B$	$BA-98-7-6-5+4321$
432A	07378	$12*(-3+456-(7+89))*(-A+B)$	$B+A+9-8*-7-65+4321$
432B	07379	$-1-23+4-(-567+8+9A)*B$	$B-A+9+8-(-7+6-5)+4321$
4330	07380	$123-45-6-78*(-9*A+B)$	$-B-A+98-7-65+4321$
4331	07381	$-1+2+34-5+6-7*89*-A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7-(-6+5)+4321$
4332	07382	$-12-3-4-(-567-(-8-9A))*B$	$BA-9-87*(-6-54)-(-32-1)$
4333	07383	$-1+23-45+6*(7*8+9*AB)$	$-B-A+9+8+7-(-6-5)+4321$
4334	07384	$-1234-5+6+7-8*-9*AB$	$-B-(-A+98)-76-(5-4321)$
4335	07385	$(1-2+3+4)^5-6*(7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A-9-(-87+65-4321)$
4336	07386	$1+2-3+45-6-7*89*-A-B$	$B-(-A+98*-76)+5*(-432-1)$
4337	07387	$-1+2-34+5-6+7*(89*A+B)$	$BA-98-7-6+5+4321$
4338	07388	$-1+2-34+56-7*89*-A+B$	$BA-9-87-6-5+4321$
4339	07389	$1+2-3+4+5*(-6*-7+8+9AB)$	$-B+A+98-(76+5)+4321$
433A	07390	$-123-4+5*(-6-(-78-9AB))$	$-B+A-9-(-8+7)-(-6*5-4321)$
433B	07391	$(-1*-2+3^4+5)/-6*(-7*8*9)+A-B$	$B-(A-98)-(-76-(-5+4321))$
4340	07392	$-1*2*(-34-5-6+7)*(89-(A+B))$	$B+A+9*8-(-7+65-4321)$
4341	07393	$1-2*(3+45*67)+8*(9-AB)$	$BA+987-65*(-43-21)$
4342	07394	$-12-3-45+6*(789+AB)$	$-B-(A-98-7)-(65-4321)$
4343	07395	$-1-2345-67-8*-9AB$	$-B+A9-(87-6-5-4321)$
4344	07396	$-12+34-56*-78-9A*-B$	$-B+A+9*(-87+6*-5-4)*3*-2-1$
4345	07397	$1-(2+3+4)-(-56+7*89*-A+B)$	$-BA+9876-5432-1$
4346	07398	$-123+45-67*(-89+A)+B$	$-BA+9876-5432*1$
4347	07399	$1-2-3*-4*(-5-6)*-7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876+5432-1)$
4348	07400	$-1234+5678-(9+AB)$	$BA-9-87+6-5+4321$
4349	07401	$1-(-2+3+4-56+7*-89*A+B)$	$BA-98+7-6+5+4321$
434A	07402	$-1+2-(-3-45-6-7*-89*-A)-B$	$B-(-A98+76*-54+3*-21)$
434B	07403	$-123+4+5*(67+8+9AB)$	$-B+A+9+87-(65-4321)$
4350	07404	$-12-34-56*7-8*9*A*-B$	$-B+A-9+8+7+6*5+4321$
4351	07405	$-12-34-5+6*(789+AB)$	$B-(A-9)-(-87+65-4321)$
4352	07406	$-12*(-3+4*5-6*(7-(-89+A+B)))$	$BA+9-(87+6+5)+4321$
4353	07407	$1-23*-45*6+7-8-9*AB$	$-BA-(-9-8765+4321)$
4354	07408	$-123-(-4567-8+9)-AB$	$-BA+98+(7+6)*5+4321$
4355	07409	$1*-2345+6789-AB$	$-B-A9+87+65+4321$
4356	07410	$1-(2345-6789+AB)$	$BA-9-(87-6-5-4321)$
4357	07411	$-1234+5678-(9A+B)$	$-B+A9*-8+765+4321$
4358	07412	$-12+3-4+56-7*-89*A+B$	$-B-(A-9)-(-8+7*-6-5-4321)$
4359	07413	$1234-56*(-78+9)-AB$	$-BA+98-7-(-65-4321)$
435A	07414	$-123+4567-(-89+A)-B$	$-B*(-A98-7+654-32-1)$
435B	07415	$-1+2+3-45-6*(-789-AB)$	$-B-A-9-8+7+65+4321$
4360	07416	$1*2*(3-4567+8*9AB)$	$B-A-(-9+8*(7-654))-32*1$
4361	07417	$1-2-34-56*(-7-(89-A)-B)$	$B+A9-8-(7+65-4321)$
4362	07418	$-1234+5678-(-9+AB)$	$BA+9-87-(-6+5-4321)$
4363	07419	$-123-(-4567-8)-(9A+B)$	$-B-A+9-8-7+65+4321$
4364	07420	$1*(2+3)*45*(67-8*9+A+B)$	$B+A98+(-76-54)*-32+1$
4365	07421	$-1234-(-5678+9)-A*B$	$B-(-A-98)-(-76-5-4321)$
4366	07422	$-123+4+5+67*8*(-9-(-A-B))$	$-B+A+9-(-8-7*6+5-4321)$
4367	07423	$-1234+5-6*-7+8*9*AB$	$B-A-9-8-7-(-65-4321)$
4368	07424	$-123+4-5-6*(-7-89A+B)$	$BA-9-8+7-65+4321$
4369	07425	$-1234-(-56+7+8*9*-AB)$	$B+A+9+87-65+4321$
436A	07426	$-123+4567+8+9-AB$	$BA-9-(-8+7)-(-65-4321)$
436B	07427	$-123-45+6*(7+89A)-B$	$BA+9-8-76+5+4321$
4370	07428	$-1-23*-4*-5*-6*7-89AB$	$BA-(-9+87)-(-6-5-4321)$
4371	07429	$-1-(2345-6789+A*B)$	$B+A-9*(8-7*-6*-5*4+3^2)+1$
4372	07430	$-1-2*(34-5)*(-67-8-9-A)+B$	$-B+A9-8*(-7+6-5+4)*321$
4373	07431	$-123-(-4567+8)-(-9-A*-B)$	$B-A9+87+65+4321$
4374	07432	$1-2+3-(-4-56)*78-9*-A*B$	$-BA9-8+7+6-5*-4*321$
4375	07433	$-1234-(-5678+9A)+B$	$-BA9-(87+6-5432-1)$
4376	07434	$-123+4567-89-(-A+B)$	$-B+A-(-9+8*7)-(-6-(-5+4321))$
4377	07435	$-123+4567+89*(A-B)$	$BA+9-8-7*(6+5)+4321$
4378	07436	$-123+4567-89-A+B$	$B*(-A+9+8*7*6-(-54+3+2))*1$
4379	07437	$-1+23-45+6*(789+AB)$	$-B+A-(9-8)-(-7-65-4321)$
437A	07438	$(-1-2*3^4+5*6)*-7*8-9+A-B$	$-BA+98+76-(-5-4321)$
437B	07439	$-1234+5678+9A*-B$	$B-(A+9)-(-8+7-65)+4321$
4380	07440	$1+2+(3-4-56)*(-7-89-A+B)$	$BA-9+8+7-65+4321$
4381	07441	$-123+4567-(-8+9A)-B$	$-B-A-(9-87+6-5)+4321$
4382	07442	$-1-2+34-(-56-7*-89*-A)-B$	$-BA9-8-76+5432-1$
4383	07443	$-1-2*34-(567-89-A)*B$	$BA+9-(-8+76)+5+4321$
4384	07444	$-12+3-(4+5)-6*(-789-AB)$	$-BA9-(87-6)-5432*-1$
4385	07445	$-12-3+4+56*-7-8*-9*-A*-B$	$-BA9-87-(-6-5432-1)$
4386	07446	$1+2+34+(567-8-9A)*B$	$-B-A+98-7-6-5+4321$
4387	07447	$-1-23+4567-89-AB$	$B+A9-(-8-7+65-4321)$
4388	07448	$-12*(-345+67-89-A-B)$	$B-A-9-8+76+5+4321$
4389	07449	$1-(23-(4567-89)+AB)$	$-B-A+9-(-87+6)-(-5-4321)$
438A	07450	$-1234-5+67+8*9*AB$	$BA-9-87*-65-432*1$
438B	07451	$12+34+5+67*8*(-9+A)*B$	$-B+A-(9-87)-(-6+5-4321)$
4390	07452	$1*-2*(-34+56*7-8)*-9*(-A+B)$	$-B+A-9+8+76-(5-4321)$
4391	07453	$1+2-34+5*(67-8+9AB)$	$B-A-9+8+7+65+4321$
4392	07454	$(-1+(-2-3)*4)*-5*(6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A-(-9+8-76+5-4321)$
4393	07455	$1+2-(3+4+5-6)*(-7*-8+9A*-B)$	$B+A+9-8*7*(-6+5)+4321$
4394	07456	$-123+4567-89-(-A-B)$	$-B+A9-8+7-6*5+4321$
4395	07457	$123-(4-56+7*-8*(9A+B))$	$B-(-A+9+8-7)-(-65-4321)$
4396	07458	$-1-23*4*5+67+8*-9*-A*B$	$-BA9-(-8-(-76+5432))-1$
4397	07459	$1-2-3+4-5-6*(-789-AB)$	$B+A-9+8-7-(-65-4321)$
4398	07460	$123+4-5*6-7*(-89+A)*B$	$-BA9-(-8+76-5432-1)$
4399	07461	$-1234+5678-9*A+B$	$-B-A+9+87+6-5+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
439A	07462	1+2-34-(-56*78-9AB)	-B+A-(9-8-76)+5+4321
439B	07463	-12-(345+6*-7-8*9*A*B)	BA-9-(8+7*6)-(5-4321)
43A0	07464	-12+3-(-4567+89)-AB	B-(A+9-8)-(-76-5-4321)
43A1	07465	123+4+56-7*8*(-9A-B)	BA98-7654+3*-21
43A2	07466	1-2+3+4+56+7*-89*-A+B	B-A+9-8+76+5+4321
43A3	07467	-123-(-4567+8*9-(A-B))	BA9-8-76*-54-(-3+2-1)
43A4	07468	-1+2*-3+4567-89-AB	B-(A+9)-(8-76)-(-5-4321)
43A5	07469	-1-2-3+4567-89-AB	-B-(A-(9+8))-(-7-65)+4321
43A6	07470	-1*(2-(-3+4567-89-AB))	-B+A+9-(-8-76-(-5+4321))
43A7	07471	1-2-3-(-4567+89+AB)	-B+A9-8-7-(6-5)+4321
43A8	07472	12+3-4-5+6*(789+AB)	-B-A+98+7+6-5+4321
43A9	07473	12-34+56*78+9AB	-B+A9-8-7+6-5+4321
43AA	07474	1*2-3+4567-89-AB	B-(A-(9+8)-(-76+5)+4321))
43AB	07475	-1-(2-3-(4567-89))-AB	B-(A+9-87-6-5-4321)
43B0	07476	-1*(2-3-(4567-89)+AB)	BA-9-(87-(65+4321))
43B1	07477	1-2-(-3-4567)-(-89+AB)	B+A+9-(-8+7-65-4321)
43B2	07478	-1+2+3-4*5+6*7*(89-A)-B	-B+A+98-7+6-5+4321
43B3	07479	-12-3-(-4567+89-A*-B)	BA-(98-7-(65+4321))
43B4	07480	-1-2*-3+4567-89-AB	B*A*(9-(8-76-5-(-43+21)))
43B5	07481	1+2+3+4567-(-89+AB)	-B+A+9-(-87-6)-(-5-4321)
43B6	07482	1-2-34-(-56*(7+89))-AB	B-A+98+7-6-5+4321
43B7	07483	-12+3+4567-8+(9+A)*-B	B+A9-87+65+4321
43B8	07484	1+2-345*6+7+8*-9A*-B	-BA+9+876+5*-43*-21
43B9	07485	-12+3+4567-89-A*B	B-(A+9)-(-87-6)-(-5-4321)
43BA	07486	12-3+4567-(-89+AB)	B+A+9-8+76+5+4321
43BB	07487	-1-2345+6+7-8*-9AB	-B+A-(9-87*(65-4))-(-3+21)
4400	07488	1*(-2-3-4)*(-5-678+9A+B)	BA-(9+8+7)-(-6+5-4321)
4401	07489	-123+4567+8*-9-(-A-B)	-B-(A9-8-(-7+6))-5+4321
4402	07490	12+3-(-4-5)-6*(-789-AB)	BA-98-(-76-5-4321)
4403	07491	12+3+456-7*-8*(-9+AB)	B*(A9+8+7-65+432*1)
4404	07492	1-(234-567*8-9AB)	B+A+9+8+76-5+4321
4405	07493	-1+2-(3+4+56*78-9AB)	B-A-(-9-(87+6+5+4321))
4406	07494	-1+23*(-4+567)+89A*-B	-BA+98*-7-6*54*(3-21)
4407	07495	-1-2+3-4-56*-78+9AB	BA-9+8*(-7+654)-3-2-1
4408	07496	1+2-3-(-4567-(-89+A*-B))	B+A*9+87-(65-4321)
4409	07497	-1-(2+3-(4-56*78))+9AB	B+A-98+765*(4+3)-2-1
440A	07498	12-34+56*(-7-8-(-9A-B))	B+A+98-7-6+5+4321
440B	07499	1-2-3-(-4+56*78)+9AB	-B+A9+8-(7-6-5-4321)
4410	07500	-1+2-(-34+567)*-8+9AB	B+A-9+8*(-7-654-3+2)*-1
4411	07501	1-2*3*(-4+5)*(-67+8-9*AB)	BA98-7654-32-1
4412	07502	1*2-3+4+56*78+9AB	BA98-7654+32*-1
4413	07503	1+23+4567-89-AB	BA98-7654-32+1
4414	07504	-1+2-3+(4+5)*(678+9-AB)	-B-(A987+6543)-21
4415	07505	12-3+4-5*(-67+8-9AB)	B-(A98+76)+5*4*321
4416	07506	-1+2-3-(-4567-8*-9+AB)	BA-(9-8-7-(-6-5+4321))
4417	07507	12-3-(-4567-(-89+A*-B))	B+A9-8-(-7+6-(5+4321))
4418	07508	1-2+3+4-5*6*(-789-AB)	BA+9-8+7-(6+5)+4321
4419	07509	-1234+5-678*(-9-(-A+B))	-BA9-8+76-5*4*-321
441A	07510	-1234+5678-9-A-B	-B-A-9+8765-4321
441B	07511	12+3+4+5*(67-(8-9AB))	-B-A+98-(7*-6-5)+4321
4420	07512	-1-23-(4567-89AB)	BA98-7654-3-21
4421	07513	12+34-5+6*(789+AB)	-B+A9+87-65+4321
4422	07514	-123+4567+89-AB	-BA-98*(76-5+4*-32+1)
4423	07515	-1-2-3+(-4-(-56-7))*(8-9+A*B)	B+A-(-9+876*5)-43*-21
4424	07516	1234+5*6*7*(-89+AB)	-B-(A+9+8)+7-(6*-5-4321)
4425	07517	-1-2+34*(-5-6+78+9A-B)	B-A-9+87*(65-4)+3-(-2-1)
4426	07518	-1-2345-(-6789-(-A-B))	-B-A+9876-5432-1
4427	07519	12-3+4567+8*-9-AB	-B-(A-9876)+5432*-1
4428	07520	1-(2345-6789+A)-B	B-A+9+87*(65-4)+3*(-2-1)
4429	07521	-1-2+3-4-5*67+8*-9*-A*B	B+A9+8-7+6+5+4321
442A	07522	-123+4567-8-9A-B	BA+9+8-7+6-5+4321
442B	07523	-12-3-4567+89AB	-B-A*(-9-8)*(7-6)-5+4321
4430	07524	-12+3-(4-56+7)*(8+9A+B)	BA-(-9-8-7+6)-5+4321
4431	07525	12-3+4567-8-9*(A+B)	B+A-98+765*(4+3)+21
4432	07526	-1-2-3456-(-789A+B)	B+A987-6543-21
4433	07527	-1+2+34-5*(-6-7)*(89+A)+B	-B+A987-(-6543-2)*-1
4434	07528	1-(2-(-3456+789A-B))	-B+A987-6543-2+1
4435	07529	-12+3-(4567-89AB)	-B+A987+6543*(-2+1)
4436	07530	-1+2-3456+789A-B	B-A*-9*87+65+4*-321
4437	07531	1-2345-(67+89*A*-B)	-BA9-8-7-(-6-5432+1)
4438	07532	1-(-2+3456-789A+B)	-B+A987-(6543-2-1)
4439	07533	-1+2*-3-4567+89AB	-BA9-(8-7-(-6+5432-1))
443A	07534	-1-2-3-4567+89AB	BA98-7654-3-2-1
443B	07535	-123+4567+89+A*-B	B+A9-(-87+65)+4321
4440	07536	1*2*3*(-4-(-5+6-78-9*AB))	BA98-7654-(3+2)+1
4441	07537	1-(23-4567+8+9+AB)	-BA9+8-7-(6-5432)+1
4442	07538	-1+2-(3-(-4567+89AB))	BA98-7654-(3-2)-1
4443	07539	-1*(2345-(6789+A)+B)	B-A-9-87*(-65+4)+3+21
4444	07540	-1-2345+6789-A+B	B-A+9876-(5432+1)
4445	07541	1*-2+3-4567+89AB	BA98-7654*(3-2)+1
4446	07542	1+23-(-4567+8)-9*(A+B)	B-A+9876-5432+1
4447	07543	12-3456-(-789A+B)	BA+98-7-65+4321
4448	07544	-123+4567-8-9+A+B	BA98-7654+3+2-1
4449	07545	-123+4567-89+A*B	BA98-7654+3*2-1
444A	07546	-1-23+4567-8-9A-B	BA+9-(-87+65)+4321
444B	07547	1-2*-3-4567+89AB	BA98-(7654+3*-2)+1
4450	07548	1-23-(-4567+8+9A+B)	-B+A-(-9-(8765-4321))
4451	07549	1*-2-3456+789A+B	BA+9-8+7-(6*-5-4321)
4452	07550	1-2-3456+789A+B	B-(A-9-8765+4321)
4453	07551	12-3-(4567-89AB)	-B+A9-8*(-7-6+5)+4321
4454	07552	-1234-(-5678+9-(A+B))	B+A987-6543+2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4455	07553	-1-(2345-67-8*9AB)	B+A*9-8*(-7-654)-3-21
4456	07554	1*-23+4567-8+9-AB	-B+A987-6543+21
4457	07555	1-23+4567-8+9-AB	BA9-8-76*(-54-3+2)*1
4458	07556	-123+4567+8+9-(-A+B)	B-A+98-7-(-65-4321)
4459	07557	-1-2-(3-4567+8)-(-9+AB)	BA+98+7-65+4321
445A	07558	-123+4567+8+9-A+B	B+A+9+8+(7+6*5^4+3)*2*1
445B	07559	1-(23-4567+89)-A-B	B-A+9+87+65+4321
4460	07560	1*-23*4*5*(67+8+9+A*-B)	-BA-9*(8-76-543)+21
4461	07561	1*-2345+6789+A+B	-BA9-(-8-(7+6))-(-5432+1)
4462	07562	-123+4567-8+9-(-A-B)	BA98-(7654+3)+21
4463	07563	-12-(-3-4567+8+9A)-B	-BA9+8+7+6+5+4321
4464	07564	1-23+4567+8-9A-B	BA-(9-(-8-(7-65)))+4321
4465	07565	12-3456+789A+B	-BA9+8+76*(54-(-32-1))
4466	07566	-123-(-4567+89-AB)	BA9+8-7+65*(43+21)
4467	07567	1*23-(4567-89AB)	BA+9*-87+654*-3*(-2-1)
4468	07568	1+23-4567+89AB	BA98-7654+3+21
4469	07569	1+2+3+4567-8-9-AB	BA98+765*-4*3+21
446A	07570	-1234-(-5678-9-A-B)	B-A+98+7+65+4321
446B	07571	1-(23-4567)-(-8-9+AB)	B-A-(-98-76)-5+4321
4470	07572	1+23*(4+56-(-78-9A))+B	-B+A9+8-7*(-6-5)+4321
4471	07573	-1-2-3+4567+8-9-AB	B+A-9-8+(7-6*5-4^3)^2/1
4472	07574	12*(3-(456+7)+89)*(A-B)	-B-A98+7-6-5*4*-321
4473	07575	-1*(2-3-4567-(-8-9A-B))	-BA9-8+7*6-5432*-1
4474	07576	1-(2-3-4567)-8-(9A+B)	B+A987-6543+21
4475	07577	-1-23+4567-89+A-B	BA98-7654+32-1
4476	07578	-1+234-56*-78-9*-AB	BA98-7654-32*-1
4477	07579	-1-23+4567-(89+A-B)	BA98-7654-(-32-1)
4478	07580	-12-(3-4567)+8+9-AB	-B+A9+8+76-5+4321
4479	07581	1-2-3+4567-89-A-B	B-A-(-98-76-5-4321)
447A	07582	123-45+6*(789+AB)	B-A*-9-8*(-7-654)+3-2*1
447B	07583	-1+2+3+4567+8-9-A-B	B-A9*8*-7+6+(5+4)*-32*-1
4480	07584	1-(-2+3-4567-(-8-9-A*B))	-B-(-A98+7*-654+321)
4481	07585	-12+3+4567-(8+9A-B)	B-(-A9-(-8+7+65)-4321)
4482	07586	1-23-(-4567-8+9A-B)	B-(-A9+8-76+5)+4321
4483	07587	1-2+3+4567-89-A-B	B+A9+8-(7-(65+4321))
4484	07588	-1+2-(-3-4567-(8-9A-B))	-B+A9+87*65-(4+321)
4485	07589	-1+23-(-4567+8+9+AB)	BA-9-8+76+5+4321
4486	07590	1*2+3+4567-(89+A+B)	-BA-98-(7+65*-43*2-1)
4487	07591	12+3+4567-8-9A-B	B+A+98+76-5+4321
4488	07592	12-3+4567-8+9-AB	BA-9*(87-(65+43))+2*-1
4489	07593	1-(2+3-4567-(8+9-AB))	B+A*-98*-7-65-(4+321)
448A	07594	-1+2-3+4567-8-9A+B	BA-9-(-87+6+5)+4321
448B	07595	-1*(-2-3-4567-8+9A+B)	-BA9+8*7-6*543*2*-1
4490	07596	-1-(2-3)-(-4567-(-8-9A)-B)	BA+9-8+7+65+4321
4491	07597	-1-(234-5-(-6+7))-8*9*-A*B	BA+9-(8-(76-5))+4321
4492	07598	12+3+4567-8+9-AB	-B-(A98-(-76+5432))+1
4493	07599	-1-(2+3-4567+89-A+B)	-BA-9-87+65*-43*-2-1
4494	07600	-1+23+4567-8-(9A+B)	-B+A9*(8-(-76+5)-(-4+32)))*1
4495	07601	1-23+4567-(89-A)+B	B+A9+87+6+5+4321
4496	07602	12*-3*(-4+56-7-89-AB)	-B+A9+8+76-5+4321
4497	07603	-1+2-3+4567-(89-A)-B	-BA9-8*-7-(6+5432)*-1
4498	07604	-1234+5*(-6-(7-89))*(A+B)	-B-A-987*-6-543+2*1
4499	07605	1*(-2+3)*4567-89+A-B	BA-9+87+(6-5)*4321
449A	07606	12-3+4-5-6*(-7-89A+B)	BA-9+87+6-(5-4321)
449B	07607	12-3+4567-8-9A+B	BA-(-9+8-(76+5+4321))
44A0	07608	-1*2*3*(4-56+78+9A*-B)	B-A98+7-(-6-5*4*321)
44A1	07609	1+23+4567-8+9-AB	B-A-9-(-876-5*-43*-21)
44A2	07610	-12-3+4567-89-(-A-B)	B+A9-(-87*65+4)-321
44A3	07611	1+2+3+4567-89+A-B	B+A9-(-87+6-(5+4321))
44A4	07612	-1+2+3+4+567*8+9*AB	-B*(A+9+8+7*6-5*-4*-32-1)
44A5	07613	1+23+4567-89-A-B	B+A9-(-87-6-(-5+4321))
44A6	07614	12+3+4567-(-8-9+AB)	BA98-7*(654-3)*2*1
44A7	07615	-1-(2-3-(4567-8*(-9+A+B)))	BA98-7654-3*-21
44A8	07616	-12+3-(-4567+89)+A+B	BA-(9-87)+6-(-5-4321)
44A9	07617	1*23-(-4567-8+9A+B)	-BA+9-87-65*-43*2-1
44AA	07618	12-3-(-4567+89A)+B	B-A98-76+5432-1
44AB	07619	-1234+5678-9*-A-B	B-A98-76-5432*-1
44B0	07620	12-34-5-6*(-7-89A)-B	BA+98+7*(-6+5)+4321
44B1	07621	-1-(2+3)-(-4567+89-A-B)	BA+98-7+6-5+4321
44B2	07622	12-(-3-4567+89-A+B)	BA+9-(-87+6-5)+4321
44B3	07623	12-3+4567-(-8+9A-B)	BA+9+8+76+5+4321
44B4	07624	-123+4567+89-A-B	-B+A-987*-6-(543-2)*1
44B5	07625	-1-(-2+3-4567)-(-89-A-B)	-B+A+9+876-5*43*-21
44B6	07626	123-4-(5+6*(-789-AB))	B-A*-9+87*(65-4)-3*2*-1
44B7	07627	-1-(2-3-4567+89-A-B)	B-A+9+876-5*-43*21
44B8	07628	1+23*-45*-6-(-78*-9+AB)	-BA-(9+87*-65)-4*-32*-1
44B9	07629	12+3+4567-(-8+9A-B)	BA+9+8*(7+654)-3+2-1
44BA	07630	1*(2+3)*(-4+5+6+78+9AB)	BA+9*-8*(7-65+4-32)*1
44BB	07631	-1-(-23-4567+89)+A-B	BA-(-98+7-6-5-4321)
4500	07632	-1+23+4567-89*(-A+B)	-BA-9*(-8-7+6*5)+4321
4501	07633	-1+23+4567-89-(A-B)	-BA+987*6-5-432*1
4502	07634	1+23*4*5*-6-(78-9)*-AB	BA+9+87+6+5+4321
4503	07635	-1*(2+3)*(-45+67*(-8-9)-AB)	BA+98+7+6-5+4321
4504	07636	123-4+5+6*(789+AB)	B-A98+76*(54+32)+1
4505	07637	12+3*4*5-6*(-789-AB)	-BA9+87-(6-5432)-1
4506	07638	-1+23+4567+8-9A+B	-BA9+8+76+5432-1
4507	07639	1*23+4567+8-9A+B	-BA9+87-(6-5432-1)
4508	07640	12-3+4+5*(6+78+9AB)	-BA9-(-8-76)-(-5432-1)
4509	07641	-1234+5678-9-A*-B	B-A*-9+8765-4321
450A	07642	1-2+3+4567+8-9*A+B	-BA9+87-6*543*2*-1
450B	07643	1-2+3+(-4-5)*(-678+9A-B)	-BA+987*6+5-432*1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4510	07644	123+4+5+6*(789+AB)	-BA9+8*(7+6)-(-5432+1)
4511	07645	-1-(23-4567)-(8-(-9-A-B))	BA+98+7+6+5+4321
4512	07646	123+4567-89-AB	-BA98+765*(43-21)
4513	07647	-1234+5678-(-9A+B)	-BA+9-87*-65+4*-32+1
4514	07648	12+3+45*-6*(-7-8-9)+A-B	BA-(-9-87*(65-4)-3+21)
4515	07649	1-(23+45)-6*(-7-(89A+B))	B-(A-987*6+543-21)
4516	07650	-1-2345+6*7+89*A*B	B-A*-9+87+65+4321
4517	07651	-123+4567-(8-9A*-B)	-BA9+87-(6-5432-1)
4518	07652	-123+4-567*-8+9AB	BA-9+87*(6+54+3*(2-1))
4519	07653	-1+23+4567-(89-(A+B))	BA+9+8*(7+654)-(3-21)
451A	07654	-123-(-4567+8)-(9-AB)	-B+A9+8*(-7+65*4*3+21)
451B	07655	-123+4567+8+9A-B	B-A+9876+5*-4*321
4520	07656	-1+2+3-(-4567-8*9)-AB	-B*(A9+87)*(-6+5-4+3-(2-1))
4521	07657	123-4+5*(67-(8-9AB))	BA9+8*(-765-4*-321)
4522	07658	-1*(23-4567-89+AB)	-B+A9+8765-4321
4523	07659	-1234+5678+9A*B	BA9+87*(-6+54)-3-21
4524	07660	-1+234-(5+6*(-789+A*-B))	B+A-9+8-7+6*5-4*3*2-1
4525	07661	-123+4567+8+9A+B	B-(-A9-87*(65-4))-(-3-(-2+1))
4526	07662	-1234+5678-9+AB	-B-A*9*-8-7*-65+4321
4527	07663	-1-23+4567-8+9-A-B	-B-A98+76+5*-4*-321
4528	07664	-1-2*3*-45+67*(-8-(9-A*B))	BA+98+7-6*-5+4321
4529	07665	-12+34-5+6*(-7+89A+B)	B+A-9-8*7+6*5-4*3*2-1
452A	07666	123-4-5*6*-78+9AB	-BA+9+8*-7+65*4*3*2+1
452B	07667	1+23+4567+8*-9*(-A+B)	-B-(-A9-87-65-4321)
4530	07668	-12-3+4567+89-AB	BA*(-9-8+7+65-4*3*2+1)
4531	07669	-1234+5678+9A+B	B+A*-98*-7-6+5-(4+321)
4532	07670	-1-2345-(-6789-AB)	-B+A987+6*(-5-4*321)
4533	07671	1*-2345-(-6789-AB)	-B-A9-8-7*6*5+4321
4534	07672	1-2345-(-6789-AB)	B-(-A+9*-8-7*6*5)+4321
4535	07673	-1+2-3-45-6*(-7-89A-B)	-B+A*98+7*(654-(-3-2+1))
4536	07674	-12-(-3-4567-89+AB)	-BA-9-87*(-65+4-3)-(2+1)
4537	07675	-1-234+5+67-8*-9*-A*-B	-B-A98-(7-(-6+5432)-1)
4538	07676	-12-3+4567-8-9A+B	B+A+9-8+7+6*5-4*3*2-1
4539	07677	-123+4567-(-8-9A-B)	-BA-9-87*(-6+5)*(43+21)
453A	07678	1-(23+456*(7+8))*(9-A-B)	B*(-A-9+87+(-6+5)*432*-1)
453B	07679	-1-2-3+4567+89-AB	-B-A9-(-87*65-4*(-3-21))
4540	07680	-1234-(-5678-9-AB)	B+A9-(-8765+4321)
4541	07681	-1-23-(-4567-8+9-A)-B	BA+9876-5432-1
4542	07682	-12-(-3-4567)-8-(9-(A-B))	BA-9+87+65+4321
4543	07683	-1+2-3+4567+89-AB	BA+9876-(5432-1)
4544	07684	-1-23-(-4567+8-9)*(A+B)	B+A+9-8*7+6*5-4*3*2*1
4545	07685	1-23+4567+8-9-A+B	-B-A98-7+6+5432-1
4546	07686	12*(-3+4+5+6*78-9*(-A+B))	-B-A98-7+6-5432*-1
4547	07687	1-23+4567-8+9-A+B	-B-A98-(7-6)-(-5432-1)
4548	07688	123+45+6*(789+AB)	-B-A98-(-7+6-5432*1)
4549	07689	-1+2-(3-4567-(-8-(-9A+B)))	-B-(A98-7)-6-(-5432-1)
454A	07690	12-(-3-4567-(-8-9-A-B))	B+A+(9-8)*7+6*5-4*3*(2+1)
454B	07691	1-2+3+4567+8-9-A-B	BA-(-9-8765)-4321
4550	07692	-12-3+4567+8-9-(A+B)	-BA-987*-6+5*4*(-3-21)
4551	07693	-1+2+3+4567-(-8+9)-A-B	B-A9-8-7*6*5+4321
4552	07694	-12-3+4567+8-9-(A-B)	-BA+9+8-7*6*5+4321
4553	07695	-123*(4-(5-6))*(7+8-9-(A+B))	B-A*-98*(7+6)-5-4321
4554	07696	12-3+4567+89-AB	B-A98-7-6-5432*-1
4555	07697	-1+2+3+4567-8-(9-(A-B))	B-A98-7-(6-5432-1)
4556	07698	-12+3+4567+8-9A-B	-BA+9-8+(7+65*43)*-2-1
4557	07699	-1-(-2-3)-(-4567+8+9)-A+B	-B-(A98-7)+6+5432-1
4558	07700	123+4567+8*-9-A*B	-B-A98-(-7-6+5432*-1)
4559	07701	-1-2-(3-4567)-(-8-(9-(A+B)))	-B-A98-(-7-6)-(-5432-1)
455A	07702	12-(-3-4567-89+AB)	-B+A-98+7*6*5+4321
455B	07703	1-23+4567-(-8-9)-A+B	-BA-9-8+7-(-65*43*2-1)
4560	07704	-12-(345-6)-7*(8-9*AB)	BA+98-7*(-6-5)+4321
4561	07705	-1+2-(-3-4567)-(-8-9+A+B)	BA9+8*7*(6+54+32-1)
4562	07706	12-3+4567-(-8+9A)+B	-BA-987-6+5432-1
4563	07707	12+3+4567-(-8+9)*A-B	-BA-987-6+5432*1
4564	07708	12+3+4567-(8-9)-(A+B)	B-A98+(-7+6)*(-5432+1)
4565	07709	-1-23-(-4567+89-AB)	B-(A98+7)-(-6-5432-1)
4566	07710	-12-(3-4567-8-9-(A-B))	-BA-987+6*543*2-1
4567	07711	123-4567+89AB	BA+98+7+65+4321
4568	07712	12-(-3-(4567-8)+9)-(A-B)	BA+98+76-(5-4321)
4569	07713	1-(-23-4567-89+AB)	B+A+9-8*7+6*5-4*3*2-1
456A	07714	-12-(3-4567-8+9-A-B)	B-(A9+8)-(-7+65)*-4*(3+21)
456B	07715	-1*(-2+3)*(-4567+8-(-9-(-A-B)))	-B-A9-(87*-65-(-43-21))
4570	07716	-123+4+5+6*7+8*-9*-A*B	B+A-9+8*7+6*5-4*3*2/1
4571	07717	12-3+4567-(-89A*B)	B+A+9-8*7+6*5-4*3/2-1
4572	07718	1-(2-3-4567-(-89-A*-B))	-BA-987+6+5432-1
4573	07719	1+23+4567-8+9-A-B	-BA-987+6+5432*1
4574	07720	-12-(3-4567)-89+AB	-BA-(987-6-5432-1)
4575	07721	-1-23+4567+8+9-(A-B)	B-A98+7+6+5432-1
4576	07722	12-3+4567+8-(9A)+B	B-A98-(7+6+5432)*-1
4577	07723	1-(-23-4567+8+9A-B)	B-A98+7-(-6-5432)+1
4578	07724	12-3+4567-8+9-A+B	B-A9*(-87+6)+54*-3*21
4579	07725	1-2-(3-4567-8-9-(-A+B))	B+A+9-8-7+6*5-4*3*2*1
457A	07726	12-3+4567-(-8+9)+A+B	BA9+8+7*6*(54+3)-21
457B	07727	-1-2-(-3-4567-(-8+9)-(A-B))	B+A9+8-7*6*-5+4321
4580	07728	-1*-2*(-3-45)*67*(8+9+AB))	-B+A*9*87-6-(54-3)*21
4581	07729	12+3+4567-(-8+9*(A-B))	-B-A98-7*-6+5432*1
4582	07730	12-(-3-(4567-(8-9A)))-B	-B+A987+6*(5-4*321)
4583	07731	-1+2-3+4567-8+9A+B	-BA+987*6-54-321
4584	07732	-1*(-2-3-4567-8-9-A+B)	BA9+8*-7-(65+4)*3*-21
4585	07733	-12-34*(-56-78)+9AB	-B*(-A9-87-65+4321)
4586	07734	123+4567-8-9-AB	-B+A-987-6+5*-4*-321

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4587	07735	$1+2+3 - (-4567-8) - (-9+A-B)$	$-B - (-A9-876+5*43*-21)$
4588	07736	$-1* (-2+3-4567+89-AB)$	$B-A9 - (8-7+65*43*-2)+1$
4589	07737	$-1+23+4567+8 - (9+A-B)$	$B-A9-87*-65-43-21$
458A	07738	$123-4+567*8+9*AB$	$-BA-9-8*(-7-6)*5+4321$
458B	07739	$1-23*4+5 - (-67-8)*9*A+B$	$-B-A+9-87-65*-43*2*1$
4590	07740	$1-2*34-567*-8+9AB$	$B+A+9+8-7+6*5-4*3-2-1$
4591	07741	$1+23+4567-8+9-A+B$	$-B+A-9-87-65*-43*-2*-1$
4592	07742	$1-2+3*45+67*8*(-9+A+B)$	$B-A9+87*65+4+3*-21$
4593	07743	$1+2+3+4567-89+AB$	$-B-A9+87*65 - (43-2-1)$
4594	07744	$12+3+4567+8+9+A-B$	$-B*(-A9-87-6-5-4-321)$
4595	07745	$-12-3+4567 - (8*-9+A) -B$	$B-A*9*8+765+4321$
4596	07746	$12+3+4567+8+9-A+B$	$-BA-9+87*65 - (-4-32*-1)$
4597	07747	$12+3 - (-4567-8 - (-9+A)*B)$	$-BA-9-876-5*4*321$
4598	07748	$12+3 - (-4567 - (8-9) - (A+B))$	$B - (A+987-6)+5*4*321$
4599	07749	$1 - (-2+3-4567-8 - (9+A) -B)$	$-B-A*9*(8-76) -5*(-43-21)$
459A	07750	$1234+5-67*8*-9-A+B$	$BA - (9-876)+5*-43*-21$
459B	07751	$(1+2+3)^(4-5+6) -7-8-9+A-B$	$B-A98+7*6-5432*-1$
45A0	07752	$123+4567-8 - (-9+AB)$	$BA9-8*-7*-6-5*43*-21$
45A1	07753	$-1+23+4567+8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9-87*(-65-4) -321$
45A2	07754	$12+3+4567-89+AB$	$-BA-9+87*65-43+21$
45A3	07755	$1+23 - (-4567-8)+9 - (-A+B)$	$BA9+876+54*-3*-21$
45A4	07756	$123+4567 - (89+A+B)$	$B+A-987-6-5*-4*321$
45A5	07757	$1+23 - (-4567-8) - (-9+A-B)$	$B+A - (-98+765*(-4-3) -21)$
45A6	07758	$-1234+5*-6+78*(9A-B)$	$-B-A9-876+5*-4*-321$
45A7	07759	$1 - (-23-4567) - (-8+9-A)+B$	$-B-A+987+6-5*43*-21$
45A8	07760	$12-3+4567 - (-8-9)+A+B$	$BA9+8+7*654-321$
45A9	07761	$123+4567+8-9A-B$	$BA98-7*(6-5-4*-321)$
45AA	07762	$-12-34-5+67*(8 - (9-A))*B$	$BA9+87*(-6+54) -3*-21$
45AB	07763	$-1-23+4567+8*(9-A+B)$	$-B - (A-987*6) - (-5 - (-432-1))$
45B0	07764	$-1*(-23-4567+89-AB)$	$-B-A9-8*(-76+54)*32*1$
45B1	07765	$1+23+4567-89+AB$	$BA-987*-6+543*(-2+1)$
45B2	07766	$12+3 - (-4567-8) - (-9-A-B)$	$BA-987*-6 - (543-2) -1$
45B3	07767	$123+4567 - (8+9A-B)$	$-B-A+9+87*65-4*-32*-1$
45B4	07768	$123+4567+8 - (-9+AB)$	$BA-987*-6-543+2+1$
45B5	07769	$123-45+6*(7+89A)-B$	$B+A-9-87*-65+4*-32*1$
45B6	07770	$-1*(-2-34)*(5+6*(-78 - (9-AB)))$	$BA9-876*-5-43*(2+1)$
45B7	07771	$-12-3-45-67-8*-9*A*B$	$B+A9-87*-65+4*3*-21$
45B8	07772	$1+23-4*(56+(78+9*A)*-B)$	$B-A9-87*-65-4 - (32-1)$
45B9	07773	$123+4567-8+9*-A-B$	$-BA+9+87*65+4*-3*2-1$
45BA	07774	$-12-3-45*(-6+7 - (8+9) -AB)$	$-BA+9-87*-65+4*-3*-2*-1$
45BB	07775	$-1+23 - (-4567-8-9-A-B)$	$-B-A-9*8*-7-65+4321$
4600	07776	$123+4567-89+A-B$	$-B-A98+76+5432-1$
4601	07777	$1+23 - (-4567-8) - (-9 - (A+B))$	$B*(-A+9+8+76-5+432+1)$
4602	07778	$-12 - (3-4567)+89 - (A+B)$	$-B-A98 - (-76-5432-1)$
4603	07779	$-1+2-3+45+6*(7+89A+B)$	$-B+A+987+6+5*43*21$
4604	07780	$-1 - (-2+34) - (567*-8-9AB)$	$-BA+9+87*65+4+3-21$
4605	07781	$12-3+4567+8*-9+AB$	$B+A+9+(87+6)*54+3+2+1$
4606	07782	$-1-23+4567-8 - (-9A+B)$	$B - (A9+8-7*65-4321)$
4607	07783	$123+4567 - (-8+9A-B)$	$-BA+9+87*65+4321$
4608	07784	$1-2 - (3+45) - (67-8*-9*-A*B)$	$B+A98+76*54+321$
4609	07785	$12-345*(67-89+A)+B$	$-BA-9-87*-65+4+3-2*1$
460A	07786	$-123-45+6*(-78+9AB)$	$B-A+9-8*(-7-6-5)*(43+2+1)$
460B	07787	$-1 - (23+4) -567*-8+9AB$	$-BA - (-9-8*-76*(54-3*21))$
4610	07788	$1+2 - (3+45+67) -8*-9*A*B$	$-B*(-A-9-8+76-543)*(2-1)$
4611	07789	$1-23 - (-4567-89) - (-A+B)$	$B-A9-87*-65+4-3-21$
4612	07790	$1*-23 - (-4567-89) - (A-B)$	$BA+987*6-543+21$
4613	07791	$1-23 - (-4567-89+A)+B$	$-B-A9-87*-65-4 - (-3 - (2-1))$
4614	07792	$-1-23+4567+8-9-A*-B$	$BA-98*(7 - (65-4)) -3 - (2+1)$
4615	07793	$-12+3 - (-4567+8+9+A*-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6*5-4+3*2/1$
4616	07794	$1-23+4567+8 - (9A*-B)$	$-BA-9-87*-65+4*3+2*1$
4617	07795	$-1-23 - (-4+567*-8)+9AB$	$-BA-987*6*(-5+4) -321$
4618	07796	$1 - (23 - (4567-8) - (9-A*-B))$	$BA+9876+5*4*-321$
4619	07797	$-1-2-345-6-78*9*-A+B$	$B-A-9*-8*7 - (65-4321)$
461A	07798	$-12 - (3 - (4567+89) -A+B)$	$B - (A98-76-5432+1)$
461B	07799	$1-23 - (-4567+8+9-AB)$	$B-A98 - (-76+5432*-1)$
4620	07800	$1 - (23-4567 - (8+9A-B))$	$B-A98+76+5432+1$
4621	07801	$-1234-56+7*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A - (9+8)*-76*5-4*32*-1$
4622	07802	$123+4*-5-6*(-7-89A)-B$	$B+A+9+8-7+6*5-4-3+2*1$
4623	07803	$123-4*(5+6+7)*(-89 - (-A+B))$	$B-A9+87*65 - (-4*-3+2*-1)$
4624	07804	$-12 - (-3-4567-89) - (-A+B)$	$-B-A9-87*-65-4*3+21$
4625	07805	$-12-3 - (-4567+8-9-A*B)$	$B - (A9+87*-65) - (4+3+2-1)$
4626	07806	$1-2+3 - (-4567+8+9-A*B)$	$-BA-9-87*-65+4-3+21$
4627	07807	$1+2*-3*(-45+6*7) - (-8-9A*-B))$	$-BA-9 - (-87-65*43*2-1)$
4628	07808	$-12-3+4567-8-9+AB$	$-BA+9+87*65 - (-4-3-2-1)$
4629	07809	$-1-2-3+4567+89+A-B$	$B-A9+87*65-4-3+2+1$
462A	07810	$1+2 - (3-4567+8) - (-9A+B)$	$BA*(98-76+5-4+3+21)$
462B	07811	$1-23+4567 - (-89-A-B)$	$B - (A9-87*65) -4+3-2+1$
4630	07812	$1-23+4567+8+9+A*B$	$B+A+9+8-7+6*5+4+3-2^1$
4631	07813	$-1-23+4567+8-9+AB$	$B-A9-87*-65+4-3-2+1$
4632	07814	$-12+3+4567-8-9+AB$	$-BA - (9-87*65+4-32*1)$
4633	07815	$1-23+4567+8-9+AB$	$-BA+987*6+5*4-321$
4634	07816	$-1*(23 - (4567-8) - (9+AB))$	$-B-A9+87 - (65*43*-2+1)$
4635	07817	$1*(2-3)*(-4567 - (89 - (A-B)))$	$-B-A9+87*65+43-21$
4636	07818	$-1*2*-3*(-45-67+8+9AB)$	$-B-A*(-98-7+65)+4321$
4637	07819	$-1+2+3+4567 - (-89-A+B)$	$-B+A - (-9 - (8-76*5+4321))$
4638	07820	$-12-3+4567+89+A+B$	$BA9-876*-5+43*-2-1$
4639	07821	$12 - (34+56+7) -8*9*A*-B$	$-BA+98-7-65*43*-2*1$
463A	07822	$1-23 - (-4567-8) - (-9A-B)$	$-B+A*9*8*7 - (65+4+3)*(-2-1)$
463B	07823	$1 - (-23-4567) - (-89+A+B)$	$-BA+9*(-8-7+654 - (3+21))$
4640	07824	$12-34*5+6*(-78+9AB)$	$B+A+9+8+7+6*5-4+3*2+1$
4641	07825	$-12-3+4567*(-8+9)+AB$	$-BA - (-9 - (87-65*43*-2+1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4642	07826	-12+3+4567+89+A+B	-B-A9-87*-65-4+32+1
4643	07827	123-4*-56*(7-8+9+A+B)	-B-A-987-6+5432-1
4644	07828	1-(2-3)+4567-(8-9+A+B)	-B-A-987-6+5432*1
4645	07829	-1-2-(34-(-56+78*9-A))*B	-B+A98-765+4321
4646	07830	-12+3+4567+8-9+AB	-B+A98-76+5*43*21
4647	07831	-12-3+4567+8-(9A-B)	B-(A9+8+7+65*43*2*-1)
4648	07832	-12+3-(-4567-(8+9)-AB)	-B-A9+87*65+4+32-1
4649	07833	1-23+4567-(8-(9+AB))	B+A-(-9-8+76)*(-5+43*-2)+1
464A	07834	12+3-(-4567-89+A-B)	B+A+9+8+7+6^5+4+3^2*1
464B	07835	123-4*-5+6*(-7+89A+B)	BA9-876-5+4321
4650	07836	12-3-(-4567+8)-(9-AB)	-B-(A9-87*(65-4))+321
4651	07837	-1*(-2-3-(4567-8+9A+B))	BA+98+7*6*5+4321
4652	07838	1+23-(-4567+8)+9A-B	B+A+9-8+7+6^5+4^3/2+1
4653	07839	12-34-56*(7-(8+9A))+B	-B-A-(987-6)-(-5432+1)
4654	07840	-1-234+5678-9AB	-B-A-987+6-5432*-1
4655	07841	1*-234+5678-9AB	-B-A-(987-6)-(-5432-1)
4656	07842	1-234-(-5678+9AB)	B+A-9+87*65+43*-2+1
4657	07843	1+23-4+567*8+9AB	B-A98*-7+6*5*-43*-2*-1
4658	07844	123+4567-8-(9+A)-B	BA9-876*-5-4-3*21
4659	07845	1+23+4567-(89+A-B)	BA9-876-(-5-4321)
465A	07846	-12+3-(4+56-7)+8*-9*A*-B	-B+A9-8*-7*-6*(-5-(-4-3)-21)
465B	07847	1+2+3+4567+8-9+AB	-B+A-987-6+5432-1
4660	07848	12-3+4567+89+A+B	-B+A-987-(-6+5432)*-1
4661	07849	12-3+4567+8+9+A*B	B-A*98*-7-6*(-5-4-32)*-1
4662	07850	1-2+3+4567+8-(9A-B)	B-A-987-6-5432*-1
4663	07851	-1+2-(-3+4-5)-(-6+7*8*(-9-AB))	B+A98-(765-4321)
4664	07852	1+2-(3-4567+8*(-9-A)+B)	B+A98-76+5*-43*-21
4665	07853	1-(-23-4567+8)-9+AB	B+A*-9-(-8+7)-65*(-43*2-1)
4666	07854	-1*(-2-(-34+5))*(-6-78-(9+AB))	B*(A-9-8)*(7-6-54-32-1)
4667	07855	1-(2+3)-(-4567-8-9-AB)	-BA-98*(-7+6-54)+321
4668	07856	123+4567+89-AB	-BA-9+87*65+43+21
4669	07857	-1*-23*(-4+56-7+89+AB)	B-A9*(8+7-65)-4*32*1
466A	07858	-1-(-23-4567+8)+9A+B	B+A+9*(87-(6-543))+21
466B	07859	-1-2+3+4567+8+9+AB	-B+A-987+6+5432-1
4670	07860	123+4567-(-8+9+A+B)	-BA-9-876+5432-1
4671	07861	-1-(-2-3-(-4-56+7))+8*-9*-A*B	B-(A+987-6-5432)-1
4672	07862	123+4567-(8-9)-A-B	-BA-(9+876)-(-5432-1)
4673	07863	1-23*-4*(56+7)+8-(9+A+B)	B-A-(9*8*7+6-(-5+4321))
4674	07864	-1+23-(-4567-8-9-A*B)	B+A-9-87*-65-4+3*-21
4675	07865	1+23+4567+89+A+B	BA-9-8-76*(-54+3-21)
4676	07866	-1-23+45-67-8*-9*-A*-B	-BA+98*76+54*-32*1
4677	07867	-1+23+4567+8-9+AB	-B+A-9-87*-65-43-2-1
4678	07868	-12*(-3-(-4+567-89-AB))	-B+A9-(87+65*43*-2)-1
4679	07869	1+23-(-4567-8)-(9-AB)	B+A-(987+6)-(-5432+1)
467A	07870	12+34-5+67*(-8+9A-B)	-B+A9-87-(-65*43*-2-1)
467B	07871	1+23-4-56-7+8*-9*A*-B	B-(-A+987+6)-(-5432-1)
4680	07872	-1*234*(5+6+7*(89-A*B))-B	-B-(A9+876)+5432*1
4681	07873	1+(-2+3+4^5-6*7)*8+9+A-B	-B-A9-(876-5432-1)
4682	07874	-1-(-23-4567-8-9A-B)	B+A9-87*-65+43+21
4683	07875	1*(-2+34-5+6*7)*89*(-A+B)	-B+A+9+8*7+6^5+4+3^2^1
4684	07876	12+3+4567+8+9+AB	B*(A9-87+65+432-1)
4685	07877	-1-2*3*(-45+6-7-89A+B)	BA-987-6+5*4*321
4686	07878	-1+23-(-4567+8*(-9-A))-B	-BA+9-876-(-5432+1)
4687	07879	-1-2+3*4567-89AB	-BA-(-9+876+5432*-1)
4688	07880	-1+23-45-(6+7)+8*9*-A*-B	-BA+9-876+5432+1
4689	07881	12+3+4-(56-7-8+9)*-AB	B+A-987+6+5432-1
468A	07882	123+4567-8+9+A-B	-BA+98+7*65+4321
468B	07883	-1+2-3*-4567-89AB	B+A-987+6+5432+1
4690	07884	123+4567-8+9-A+B	BA-9-87-65*43*-2*1
4691	07885	1+2-(-3*4567+89AB)	B+A+9-87*-65-43-21
4692	07886	123-(-4567+8+9-A-B)	BA9-876*-5-4*3-21
4693	07887	1*(23-(4567+89-A))*-B	-B*(-A-987-(-65-432-1))
4694	07888	-1-23+4567-(8*-9-AB)	-B-A*9*-87-(6-(5+4))*-321
4695	07889	-1-2*-3*-4*5+6*(-78+9AB)	BA-987+6-5*4*-321
4696	07890	12+34-5-67-8*9*A*-B	B-A-9+87*65-(-4-(-32+1))
4697	07891	12+3+45-67*(-8-9A+B)	B+A9-87-65*43*2*-1
4698	07892	-123+45+6*(-78+9AB)	B+A9*8*7-(65-4)*3*(-2-1)
4699	07893	1+2-3+4567-8*-9-A*-B	B-A9-876+5432-1
469A	07894	-1-23*-456-7-8*9*AB	B-A9-876+5432*1
469B	07895	(-1-2/3+4)*(-5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B	B-A9-(876-5432)+1
46A0	07896	12-3*-4567-89AB	B+A+9*-87*-6-543*(-2-1)
46A1	07897	-12-(3-4567)-(-8*9-AB)	-B+A9+87*65+4*32*-1
46A2	07898	-1-23+4567+89-A*-B	B-A+9+87*65-4-32-1
46A3	07899	1*-23-(-4567-89)-A*-B	-B+A*(-98+7)-6*5*4*-3*-21
46A4	07900	1-23+4567+89+A*B	-BA+9-87*-65+43*-2*-1
46A5	07901	1+234*56-(-7-89*-AB)	-BA+9+87*(-65+43)*(-2-1)
46A6	07902	123-(-4567-8+9-A-B)	B+A-9-(-87*65+4)-32+1
46A7	07903	123+4567*(-8+9)-(-A-B)	BA+9-(87+65*43*-2-1)
46A8	07904	1-2+3-(4-56)-7*-8*(9+AB)	-B+A*98+7*(65+32-1)
46A9	07905	-1+2+3*-4-5-6+7+8*-9*A*-B	-BA-(-9+876*5)+4*321
46AA	07906	(-1+2*3+4^5-6*7)*8+9-(A-B)	B+A*-98*7-(6-5-4)*3*-21
46AB	07907	1*234-5+67*8*(-9+A+B)	BA+9-87*-65-(4+3)*21
46B0	07908	-12-3456-7+89*AB	-B-(A+9+(8+76))*(-5-43-21))
46B1	07909	-12-3+4567+89+A*B	B+A+9-87*-65-43-2+1
46B2	07910	1*(-2-3)*(-456-7-8*9A+B)	B+A+9-87*-65+43*(-2+1)
46B3	07911	-12-3*45*6-(-7*89A+B)	-B+A*-9-(876-5432*1)
46B4	07912	(-1*-2*-3-4^5+6*7)*-8+9+A-B	B+A+9*8-76*-5+4321
46B5	07913	-1234-56-7*(-8-9AB)	BA-9-87*-65+4*-32+1
46B6	07914	1-(-2-(3+4567)-8)+9*(A+B)	-B-A+98+76*5+4321
46B7	07915	-12+3+4567+89+A*B	BA9+876*5+4*(-3-(-2+1))
46B8	07916	(1-(2-3)+4)^5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B	-BA-9+8*765-(432-1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
46B9	07917	$1-2-3*456-78*(-9A+B)$	$-B-A-987*-6+5-4-321$
46BA	07918	$-1+2+3+4567-8*-9+AB$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^5+4^3*2-1$
46BB	07919	$-1-(23-4567)-(-89-AB)$	$B+A9+(8-76)*-5+4321$
4700	07920	$-1*(2+3+456+78-9-A)*-B$	$B*(-A+9-8)*(-7-65-(-4-3)-(2+1))$
4701	07921	$1-23+4567+89+AB$	$-B+A98+7-6-5*-43*21$
4702	07922	$-12-3456+7+89*AB$	$BA+987+6-5*-43*21$
4703	07923	$-1+2-3456-7-89*-AB$	$B-A-9+87*65*(-4+3)*(-2+1)$
4704	07924	$-1+2+3+4+5*-6-7+8*9*A*B$	$-B-A*98*-7-(-6-54*-3-2+1)$
4705	07925	$12-3+4567-(-8*9-AB)$	$-B-A9+8*765-432-1$
4706	07926	$1*-2*3*(4*5-(6-7+8+9AB))$	$-B-A9+8*765+432*-1$
4707	07927	$-12-(345-67*89)+AB$	$-B+A-(-987*6+5)-4-321$
4708	07928	$1-2-(-3-4567)+89+A*B$	$B-A-(-9*(-8-7+65)-4321)$
4709	07929	$-1-23-45-6*(78-9AB)$	$-B-A*98+7*(-6+5-43)*-21$
470A	07930	$-12-3+4567+89+AB$	$BA-98+(-7-6)*(5-43+21)$
470B	07931	$12-34-(5-6*7)-8*-9*-A*-B$	$B*(A-9)*(876-54-321)$
4710	07932	$1+2+3-(-4567-89+A*-B)$	$-BA-9-8*-765-432-1$
4711	07933	$123+4567-8*-9-A-B$	$-B+A98+7+6-5*-43*21$
4712	07934	$12-345+67*89-A*-B$	$BA-98-(-7*65-4321)$
4713	07935	$1-2-3456+7+89*AB$	$B+A+9-87*-65-43+21$
4714	07936	$-12+3-(-4567-89)+AB$	$B+A+9+8-7+6^5+4^3*2+1$
4715	07937	$-1+2-(3456-7-89*AB)$	$-BA+9-(-8-7)*(65+4+321)$
4716	07938	$-1-2-345+67*89+AB$	$B+A987+6*-54*(3+21)$
4717	07939	$1+2-(3456-7+89*-AB)$	$B+A+9*8+7+6^5+4^3*2+1$
4718	07940	$12+3456+(-7-8)*(-9-AB)$	$B-A*-98-7*(-654-32-1)$
4719	07941	$123+4567-8*9+AB$	$B-(-A98+7)+6-5*-43*21$
471A	07942	$-1+2-345+67*89+AB$	$B*(A-9+876-54-321)$
471B	07943	$1-2-3+4567+89+AB$	$-B-A9+87*65+4*-32*-1$
4720	07944	$1-(-2+345-67*89)+AB$	$BA-9-8-76*-5+4321$
4721	07945	$-1+2-3+4567-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A+987*6-(-5-4)-321$
4722	07946	$1-(23-45)-(-6+7)+8*-9*-A*B$	$-BA+9+87*(6+54+3+2+1)$
4723	07947	$12-3-4*(-5+6*-78-9AB)$	$BA9-876*-5-4*-3*-2*-1$
4724	07948	$1*-2+3+4567+89+AB$	$-B+A9-87*-65+43*-2+1$
4725	07949	$1-2+3+4567+89+AB$	$BA-(-9-8*-7)+65*-43*2*-1$
4726	07950	$-1*-2*-3*-45*(6-7-(89-AB))$	$BA9+8+7*(654-32)-1$
4727	07951	$-1+2+3-(-4567-89-AB)$	$B+A9-8-76*-5+4321$
4728	07952	$-1+23+4567+89-A*-B$	$-BA*(-98-7+65-4-3-2-1)$
4729	07953	$1+2-(-3-4567-89-AB)$	$-B+A9-(-876-54)*-3*-2-1$
472A	07954	$1+23+4567+89-A*-B$	$-B-(-A9-8*76)-(-5-4321)$
472B	07955	$-123-4-5*6*-7-8*9*A*-B$	$-BA+9*-876-543*-21$
4730	07956	$1*-2*(34-(-5+6))*(78-9-(-A+B))$	$-B-A+98+7-65*43*-2*1$
4731	07957	$1-(-2+3)-(-45-6*(-78+9AB))$	$-B+A9-8-7-65*-43*2*1$
4732	07958	$12-3+4567+89+AB$	$B-A-(987*6-5*4)-321$
4733	07959	$12-3*(-4+5)*-6+7+8*-9*-A*B$	$B-A-(-9+87*65)-(-4-(-3+21))$
4734	07960	$(-1+2^3)*(4^5-((6-7)*8-9))-(-A-B)$	$BA-9+8-76*-5+4321$
4735	07961	$-12+3+45+6-7+8*-9*A*-B$	$BA-9-87*(6-5)*(-43-21)$
4736	07962	$-1-(2+34)-5-6*(78-9AB)$	$-B-A-9-87*-6+5+4321$
4737	07963	$1-23-(-4+56*7*-8-9)-AB$	$B+A+9+87*65-4+3-(-2-1)$
4738	07964	$12+3+4567+89+AB$	$B*(A-9)*(-8*7-6*5*(-43+21))$
4739	07965	$-1-(-2-34*-5)-(-67*89+AB)$	$BA-9-8-(-7+65)*4*(-3-21)$
473A	07966	$123+4-(-5+67)*-89-(-A-B)$	$-BA-9*-876+5*432*-1$
473B	07967	$-1-(2+3-45*-6+78*9*-A-B)$	$B-(-A9-(8-76*-5)-4321)$
4740	07968	$12-3-45-6*(78-9AB)$	$-B-A*(9-87+65-4)*32-1$
4741	07969	$-1-23+4567+89A*-B$	$B-(-A+9)-(-87*65-4-(-3+21))$
4742	07970	$-12+3+456-7*89*-A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7+6^5+4^3*(2+1)$
4743	07971	$1-234-(-5678-9A*-B)$	$-B-A+9+87*65-(-43-2)-1$
4744	07972	$1+234-(5-678*(9+A-B))$	$BA9-876*-5-(-43+2*1)$
4745	07973	$-1+23+4567-(-89-AB)$	$-B+A*9*87-(6+5+43*21)$
4746	07974	$1*2*3*(-4-5-(-67-89A)-B)$	$-B+A+9-87*-65-4+32+1$
4747	07975	$1+23+4567+89+AB$	$-B*(A+9-87-6+54-3)*21$
4748	07976	$-1-(-234-5)+6*(-7+89A+B)$	$B-A9+8*76-(-5-4321)$
4749	07977	$-1+2+3-45*6+78*9*A+B$	$-BA-98*(-76-5*-4)-3+2*1$
474A	07978	$1+2*-3*45-67*-89*(-A+B)$	$BA+9+8+76*5+4321$
474B	07979	$12-34-5+6*(-78+9AB)$	$BA9-87-6-5*43*-21$
4750	07980	$-12*(-3-(4+567))-(-89-AB))$	$-B-(A-987*6-(54-321))$
4751	07981	$123+4567-8+9A-B$	$-B-(A+9-(-876+5432))-1$
4752	07982	$-12-3-45-6*(7+89A)*-B$	$-B+A-9-87*-6-(-5-4321)$
4753	07983	$-1+2-3-4+(-567+8-9)*-A-B$	$-B-(A+9)-(876-(5432+1))$
4754	07984	$1*234+5+6*(7+89A)-B$	$B-(-A98*76+5*-43*21)$
4755	07985	$-1-23*4*5*6+78*(-9+AB)$	$-BA+98*76-543*(2+1)$
4756	07986	$123+4567+89-(-A+B)$	$-B*(A9-87-6-543+21)$
4757	07987	$1-2-345-(678*-9+AB)$	$-B-A9*(8+7-6+5-43-21)$
4758	07988	$123+4567+89-A+B$	$BA-9+87*65-43-21$
4759	07989	$-1+2-345+678*9-AB$	$BA9-8-765+4321$
475A	07990	$-1*2*(-3+4)*567*(89-A*B)$	$-B+A-(-9+87*-6+5-4321)$
475B	07991	$123+4567-(-8+9)-A*-B$	$BA9-87-(-6-5*43*21)$
4760	07992	$12-3-(-456+7*-89*A+B)$	$-B-A*98-76-(-5432+1)$
4761	07993	$12-345-6-7*(8-9A)*B$	$-BA+98*76+5*(-4-321)$
4762	07994	$123-(-4+567*-8-9AB)$	$-B+A*-98-76+5432+1$
4763	07995	$-1+234-5+6*(7+89A)+B$	$BA-987+6*-543*2*-1$
4764	07996	$123+4567-8-9+AB$	$-B-(-A9-87*65)-(-43-2*-1)$
4765	07997	$123+4567+8+9A-B$	$BA98-7654+321$
4766	07998	$1234-56*-78-(9+AB)$	$B+A+9*(8+7)+6^5+4^3*2*1$
4767	07999	$123-456+7*(-8+9A)*B$	$BA9-876*-5+43+21$
4768	08000	$-1+23+45-6-(-7-8*-9*A*-B)$	$-B-(A-9)-(876+5432*-1)$
4769	08001	$(1-2+3-(-4*5)^6/(7-8+9))+((A-B))$	$-B-A+9-876+5432+1$
476A	08002	$-123-(-4-5678)-9AB$	$BA-987+6+5432-1$
476B	08003	$123-(-4567+8-9A)+B$	$-BA-987+6-5432*-1$
4770	08004	$-1-2*34*5-67*-89-A*-B$	$BA-(987-6)-(-5432-1)$
4771	08005	$-12+3*(-4567+8*9A*B)$	$BA9+8-765+4321$
4772	08006	$-1-2-(345+678*-9)+A*-B$	$BA+9-87*-65-43-21$
4773	08007	$1*(234-567)*(8+9)*(A-B)$	$-B-A*(98+7)-6+5432*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4774	08008	$12^*(-34-(-5-6-7))^*(89-AB)$	$B^*(-A9+87)^*(-65+43-2^*1)$
4775	08009	$1234-56^*-78-9A-B$	$B-A+98^*76+54^*32^*-1$
4776	08010	$123-4-56^*(7-8-9A)-B$	$-B+A98+76+5^*-43^*-21$
4777	08011	$12-3-4+5+6+7+8^*-9^*-A^*B$	$B-A9+8^*(76+5)+4321$
4778	08012	$123-(-4567-8)-(-9-AB)$	$B-(-A-9)-(-87^*6+5-4321)$
4779	08013	$12+3+(45-678)^*-9-AB$	$-B+A98-7^*-654-3-21$
477A	08014	$123+4567-8-(-9-AB)$	$-B+A9-87^*-65+4-32-1$
477B	08015	$1-2-3^*-4^*56-7^*8^*(-9A-B)$	$BA+987^*6-(54+321)$
4780	08016	$-1-2+3+567^*(8-9)^*-A-B$	$-B+A9-876-5^*-4^*321$
4781	08017	$1-(2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7)^*8-9-(A-B)$	$B+A9-(87^*-65-(-43-(2+1)))$
4782	08018	$123-4+5+6+7^*-8^*(-9-AB)$	$-B+A9-8+7^*65+4321$
4783	08019	$123+4567+8+9A+B$	$-B+A9+9-876+5432-1$
4784	08020	$-123+4^*56+7+8^*-9^*A^*-B$	$-B+A9+9-(876-5432^*1)$
4785	08021	$1-(2-(3-4^*-5+67))^*8^*9^*A^*B$	$B-A-(-9+876)-(-5432+1)$
4786	08022	$-1^*2^*3^*(-4+5-67-89A+B)$	$B-A-(-9+876+5432^*-1)$
4787	08023	$-1+234-(5-67)^*(89A+B)$	$B-(-A+9+876-5432+1)$
4788	08024	$-12+3+45+6+7-89^*(-A-B)$	$BA9-876^*-5-43^*-2-1$
4789	08025	$1^*(2+3+4^*5+6^*7+8)^*(9A-B)$	$B+A-(9+876)-(-5432-1)$
478A	08026	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7))^*8+9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+9+876^*5-4^*-321$
478B	08027	$1+2^*(3+4-5-6^*7^*(89-A-B))$	$B+A+9+(8+7+6-5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
4790	08028	$1^*2^*-3^*(-4-5-(-6-78)-9AB)$	$B+A^*-98^*-7-65-43+21$
4791	08029	$-1+2-(3-4-5)^*(67+89A-B)$	$BA-9+87^*65+4-32-1$
4792	08030	$123+4567+8+9A+B$	$-B^*(-A+98-76-543+21)$
4793	08031	$1234-56^*-78-(9A-B)$	$BA-(9+876-5^*4^*321)$
4794	08032	$-12+3+456-7+(8+9)^*AB$	$-B+A98^*7-65^*(-4^*-3+21)$
4795	08033	$12+3+4+56-7+8^*9^*A^*B$	$BA-(9+8+7^*-65-4321)$
4796	08034	$1-23^*-4+5^*(-6+7)-8^*9^*A^*-B$	$B+A9-87^*-65-(-4^*-3+21)$
4797	08035	$-1+2+3+4-5+6^*(-7+8+9AB)$	$B+A98-7^*-654-3-21$
4798	08036	$-12^*(-3+4-5-6+7+8-9)^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A^*98^*7+6^*54-321$
4799	08037	$123^*(4+5+6-7-8+9)+A^*B$	$-B+A98-7^*-654-3-2+1$
479A	08038	$12+3+456-7-89^*(-A-B)$	$B+A9-876+5^*-4^*-321$
479B	08039	$-12-3+4^*5-(-6+7-8)^*-9^*-AB$	$-B+A^*-98^*-7-(6+5+4-3+2+1)$
47A0	08040	$-1-2+3+4^*5^*-6^*-7-(-8-9)^*(-A-B)$	$B+A9-8+7^*65+4321$
47A1	08041	$-1^*(-2+3+4+5-6+7+8^*-9^*-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9-876+5432-1$
47A2	08042	$-12+3+4^*(-5-67)-8^*-9AB$	$-B+A98+7^*65+4+3-2^*1$
47A3	08043	$1+2+3+4+5-6^*-7+8^*-9^*A^*-B$	$B+A+9-876+5432+1$
47A4	08044	$12+3+4^*-5-6-7+8^*9^*-A+B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^*2^*1$
47A5	08045	$123+4+5^*6-7^*8^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A+98-7^*-65+4321$
47A6	08046	$-123+4+5+6+7+8+9-AB$	$-BA9-87^*-65-4^*-321$
47A7	08047	$1^*-234-(-56-7^*(8+9^*AB))$	$-B+A9+8^*(-7+65)+4321$
47A8	08048	$1-2-3+4+5-(-6+7+8^*9^*-A^*B)$	$-B+A98-7^*(-654-3-2^*-1)$
47A9	08049	$-123+4^*-5+6+7+8+9AB$	$BA+9-876+5^*-4^*-321$
47AA	08050	$-1-23+4+5+6+7^*(89-A+B)$	$B-(-A+9-(876^*5-4^*-321))$
47AB	08051	$-12+3^*-4^*(-56+7+8)-9AB$	$B-A+9+8^*(7+65)+4321$
47B0	08052	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4+5)^*(6^*7+8+9+A^*B)$	$B^*(A-(9-876+5^*-43^*-2+1))$
47B1	08053	$-1-(-23+4^*56)+7+8^*9^*A+B$	$-B-A-9+87^*65-4^*-32^*1$
47B2	08054	$1/2^*3^*4^*5^*6^*7^*8-9A+B$	$-B-A-9+8^*76-5+4321$
47B3	08055	$-1-2^*-3^*-4+5-6+7^*(-8+9A-B)$	$B+A^*98^*7-(65+4-(-3^*-2-1))$
47B4	08056	$-1-2-3^*(4+5+6)+7+8^*-9^*-A-B$	$B-(-A9-8-7^*65-4321)$
47B5	08057	$1+(-2-(3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7))^*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A-9-(8^*-765-(-432+1))$
47B6	08058	$-123+4-5-6-7+8^*9^*-A+B$	$-BA-987^*-6+54^*-3-2^*1$
47B7	08059	$12+3+4-(5+6^*(78-9AB))$	$BA-987^*-6-5^*4-321$
47B8	08060	$-1+2+3^*-4-(-567+8+9AB)$	$BA-9-87^*-65-4-3+2+1$
47B9	08061	$-123-4+5-6+7+8^*9^*A+B$	$BA-9^*-8+(7-65+43^*2)^*-1$
47BA	08062	$-12+3^*-4^*-5+6-7+8^*9^*(A+B)$	$BA-9+87^*(6+5)^*(4+3)+2^*-1$
47BB	08063	$-1-2-3-4-(5+6)^*7^*-8+9-(-A-B)$	$B^*(-A9-(87-654)-(-32+1))$
4800	08064	$1^*(2+3-4)^*(5+6+7)^*8^*(-9+9A+B)$	$B-A^*98+7^*-6-(-5432-1)$
4801	08065	$1-(-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+5-6)-(-7-8^*9)))+A-B$	$B+A-(9+8-7^*-6^*-54^*3+2+1)$
4802	08066	$123+4+5^*(-6+7+8+9A+B)$	$B-A-98^*(-7-(-6+5))+4321$
4803	08067	$-1+2+3+4+5+6^*(-7+8+9AB)$	$-B-A^*-98^*7+6^*-5-4^*3^*(2-1)$
4804	08068	$12+3+4^*5-6^*(-7+8+9A)^*-B$	$BA+9+87^*65-(4^*3+2^*1)$
4805	08069	$-1-((-2+3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7))^*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A98-7^*-654-3^*2^*-1$
4806	08070	$-1^*-2^*-3^*(-4+5^*6-7^*-8-9AB)$	$B+A9-(87^*65^*(4-3-2)+1)$
4807	08071	$-1-23+4+5+6+7+8+9+A^*B$	$B+A^*98^*7-(6+5+4+3-2)^*1$
4808	08072	$-1+2^*-3+4^*5+6+7+8+9-AB$	$BA-9^*87^*-6+54^*(32-1)$
4809	08073	$-1^*-2+3^*(4+5+6+7+8+9A+B)$	$-B-A^*98^*-7+6-54-3+21$
480A	08074	$12-3+4+5-6^*(78-9AB)$	$-B-(-A+9+8^*-76-(-5+4321))$
480B	08075	$1-23^*-4^*(5+6+7)-8-9^*-A^*-B$	$-B-(-A9-87^*65)-(-43+21)$
4810	08076	$-1^*(23+4+5+6+7^*(8-9A)^*B)$	$B-A+9+8^*76+5+432^*-1$
4811	08077	$1-(23+4+5+6+7^*(-8+9A)^*B)$	$BA+98+76^*5+4321$
4812	08078	$1+23+4-(-5+6+7)^*-8+9(A+B)$	$B+A-9+8^*76+5+432^*-1$
4813	08079	$12-3^*4^*(-56+7+8)-9AB$	$-B-(A9+8^*-765)-(-4+321)$
4814	08080	$-1^*2^*3^*(4+5+6+7+8)^*(A-B)$	$B-A^*-98^*7-65+43-21$
4815	08081	$-1-23+4+5-6+7^*-8+9A+B$	$B+A^*-98+76+5^*-4^*-321$
4816	08082	$1^*2^*3^*(-4-5-(-6+7-8-9AB))$	$B+A9+87^*65-4^*-3-(2-1)$
4817	08083	$-1-(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9)-AB$	$B-A^*(98+7-654)-3+21$
4818	08084	$1^*-23-4+5+6+7+8+9-AB$	$-B+A9^*8-7-6-5^*4^*-321$
4819	08085	$123-(-456+7+8^*-9-AB)$	$-B^*(A-(98-76+5))^*(-4-(-32-1))$
481A	08086	$1^*(-2+3+4^{\wedge}5-6-7)^*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A^*-9^*8+7+6-5+4321$
481B	08087	$1-23^*4^*(-5-6+7+8)+9-AB$	$-B+A98-7^*(-654-3)+21$
4820	08088	$-1-23+4-(-56+7+8-9AB)$	$BA+9+87^*65+4-(-3-(-2+1))$
4821	08089	$-1^*(23+4+5+6+7+8+9A+B)$	$BA-9^*(-87-6^*5^*(43-21))$
4822	08090	$1-2^*3+4+5+6+7+8-9AB$	$-B+A+9+87^*65-(4^*-32+1)$
4823	08091	$123-4^*5+6^*(78-(-9+9A+B))$	$BA-98^*(7-6)^*-5+4321$
4824	08092	$-123-4+5-6+7^*-8+9-(-A-B)$	$B-A^*98^*-7-(-6-5+43-2+1)$
4825	08093	$-1^*(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7+8/9)+A-B$	$BA9-8+7+6-5^*-43^*21$
4826	08094	$-123-4^*(-56+7-8+9A)-B$	$-BA-(-9+8^*-765)-(-4+321)$
4827	08095	$12+3+4+5-6^*(-7-8+9A+B)$	$B+A9+87^*65+4^*3^*2^*1$
4828	08096	$-1+2^*3+4^*-5+6+7+8+9A+B$	$B+A9+87+65^*43^*2-1$
4829	08097	$123+4+5+6+7+8+9-A^*-B$	$B+A+9-(-8^*76+5+432-1)$
482A	08098	$1-2^*3+4^*5+6-(-789A-B)$	$B-A-(9^*876+543^*-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
482B	08099	$1-2^* - 345+6^*(7-89-A)^* - B$	$-B-A98^* - 7+654^* - 3-2^* - 1$
4830	08100	$1^* - 2^*(3-45)^*(67-(8-9)-(A-B))$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}A(3+2-1)$
4831	08101	$1-23+(-45+678)^* - 9^*(A-B)$	$B-A9+8^*765-4-321$
4832	08102	$-1-234+5+67^*89+AB$	$-B+A+9-8^* - 76+5+4321$
4833	08103	$12-3-4-(5+6)^* - 78^*(9+A-B)$	$B+A9-(-87^*65-4)-(-3-21)$
4834	08104	$1-234+5+67^*89+AB$	$B-A+9^*876-5^*(432+1)$
4835	08105	$-1+2^*3^*45+6^*(7-8)^*9A^* - B$	$-BA+987^*6+5-4^*32^*1$
4836	08106	$-12^* - 3^*(-4+5)^*(67-(8+9-AB))$	$B-A^*98-(-7-6+5432)^* - 1$
4837	08107	$1+2^{\wedge}3^*4^{\wedge}5-6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(8-(-7+6+543-21))$
4838	08108	$((-1+2^{\wedge} - 3)^* - 4^{\wedge}5+6+7-8)^*9+A-B$	$BA-(-9+87^* - 65-(43-21))$
4839	08109	$-1+23^*4^*56-(-789+AB)$	$-B-A9-87+654^*3^*(2+1)$
483A	08110	$-1^* - 2^{\wedge}3^*4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$B-A+9^*876+5^* - 432+1$
483B	08111	$1+23^*4^*56+789-AB$	$B-A+98^*(-7+65)-4-3-2-1$
4840	08112	$1-(2+3^* - 45^* - 6^* - 7-8-9AB)$	$BA-9+87^*65-(-43+2+1)$
4841	08113	$1-234-5^*6+7^*(8-9A)^* - B$	$B-A9-(-87^*65-4^*3^*21)$
4842	08114	$-1+2^* - 345-67^*(-8-(9A-B))$	$-B-A+98^*76+5^*(-4-321)$
4843	08115	$-12-34+5678-9AB$	$-B-A^*9^* - 8-7^* - 6-5+4321$
4844	08116	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7/8+9+A-B$	$-BA+98^*7+65+4321$
4845	08117	$1-23^*4^*56-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-A-(-9-87)^*(65-4)+32^* - 1$
4846	08118	$123-(-4567-(89+AB))$	$B+A^*9^*8+7-(-6-5-4321)$
4847	08119	$-1+234^*(-5-6+7)-8^* - 9^*AB$	$-B-A^* - 98^*7-(-6+5)^*4-(-3-2-1)$
4848	08120	$12^*(-34-567-8+9AB)$	$BA+98+7+65^* - 43^* - 2+1$
4849	08121	$-1+2-(345+678^* - 9)-(A-B)$	$B-A-9-8^*(-76-5)+4321$
484A	08122	$1234-5+6^*(78+9)^*A+B$	$B+A9+87^*6-5+4321$
484B	08123	$-123-4+5678+9A^* - B$	$B+A9-87^* - 65+43+2-1$
4850	08124	$-12-3^* - 4^*(-56-7^* - 89)+A^*B$	$B-A+98^*7-(-65+432)-1$
4851	08125	$12+3^*4^*(5+6^*78)+9AB$	$-B-A+98^*(-7+65)+43-21$
4852	08126	$1234+56^*78+9-A-B$	$B-A^*(98-7-654)-3^*21$
4853	08127	$-1^*(2+34-(5678-9AB))$	$-B+A9+87^*(65-(-4+3))-21$
4854	08128	$123+4^*(5+6)-7-8^* - 9^*A^*B$	$-B-A98+7^*(65+4321)$
4855	08129	$-1+2^*34^*(-56-7)+89A^*B$	$-B-(-A9+876)+5432-1$
4856	08130	$-1+2-34+5678-9AB$	$-B+A9-876+5432^*1$
4857	08131	$1^*2-34-(-5678+9AB)$	$-B+A9-876-(-5432-1)$
4858	08132	$1+2-(-34-5678+9AB)$	$-BA+987^*6-5^* - 4^* - 3^* - 2^* - 1$
4859	08133	$12-3^*456+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B-A-98^*(-7-6)^*5+432^*1$
485A	08134	$1234-5^* - 678-9A^* - B$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^{\wedge}5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
485B	08135	$1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6/(7-8))-9+A-B$	$-B-A9+8^*(765-43)-(-2-1)$
4860	08136	$-1-2^*3^*45^*6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B-A9^* - 8^*7+654+3^* - 2+1$
4861	08137	$-1-23-(-4-5678+9AB)$	$B+A+9^*8+7^*6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}1$
4862	08138	$-1-(-2+3456+7)+89A^*B$	$BA9+8+7^*6-5^* - 43^*21$
4863	08139	$1-23-4-(-5678+9AB)$	$-BA+9-8+76^*(5-43)^*2^* - 1$
4864	08140	$12-345+67^*(8-9A^*B)$	$B-A^* - 98^*7+6+5-(-4+3)-2-1$
4865	08141	$-1-23456+7^* - 8^*9^* - A^*B$	$-B+A9^*(87+6-(-5+43))+21$
4866	08142	$-1-2^*345^*6-(-7+89A^* - B)$	$BA9+8-7^* - 654+3^* - 21$
4867	08143	$12-34+5678-9AB$	$B-A+987-(-6-5)^*(432-1)$
4868	08144	$1^* - 23-456-7^*(-89A+B)$	$BA-9-(876-5432+1)$
4869	08145	$-1-23+4-(-5678+9AB)$	$BA-9-876+5432^*1$
486A	08146	$-1+234+567^*8+9AB$	$BA-9-876-(-5432-1)$
486B	08147	$1-23+4+5678-9AB$	$-BA9+8^*76+5^* - 4^* - 321$
4870	08148	$-12-3-4+5678-9AB$	$B+A-98^* - 76+543^*(-2-1)$
4871	08149	$1-2-34-(-5-(67^*89+A^* - B))$	$-BA-98+7+6^*(5+43)^*21$
4872	08150	$-1-2-(-3^*4^*567+8+9AB)$	$BA+98^*76+54^*32^* - 1$
4873	08151	$12-3456-7+89A^*B$	$B+A9-876-(-5432+1)$
4874	08152	$-1-(-2+3456-7)-89A^* - B$	$-BA-987^* - 6-5^* - 4^*(-3-2)^*1$
4875	08153	$-1+2+3^*4-(-56-(7-8+9))^* - A^* - B$	$B+A9-876-(-5432-1)$
4876	08154	$-12+3-4+5678-9AB$	$-B-(-A-98+7^*6^* - 54^*3+21)$
4877	08155	$-12-3^*4^* - 567-(-8+9AB)$	$-B-A^*(9+87-654)+3^*2^*1$
4878	08156	$-12-3+4+5678-9AB$	$B+A+9-(8+(-7-6)^*5^{\wedge}4)+3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
4879	08157	$-123-(-45-6-78^*9^*A)-B$	$B-A98-7^* - 65^*(-4-3+21)$
487A	08158	$-1+2+3^* - 4-(-5678+9AB)$	$-BA9-87^* - 6-(-5432+1)$
487B	08159	$-1-2-3-4+5678-9AB$	$-BA9-87^* - 6+5432^*1$
4880	08160	$-1^*(2-(-3-4+5678-9AB))$	$-B-A^*(98-765+4^*32)+1$
4881	08161	$1-2-3-4+5678-9AB$	$B-A^* - 98^*7-6^* - 5+4-(-3-(-2+1))$
4882	08162	$12^*(-34-5-(-6-78))^*(9-A)^* - B$	$BA-(-9+876)-(-5432+1)$
4883	08163	$-1+2-(3+4)+5678-9AB$	$BA+9+(876-5432)^* - 1$
4884	08164	$-1^*(-2-(-3-4+5678-9AB))$	$B+A-9-876+5432+1$
4885	08165	$-1-2+3-(4-5678+9AB)$	$B-A-(-987^*6-5^* - 43)+21$
4886	08166	$-1-2-3^* - 45+6^*(-78+9AB)$	$BA+98+7^*65+4321$
4887	08167	$-1-2-(-3-4-5678+9AB)$	$BA-(9+87^* - 6^*(5-(-4-(3+2-1))))$
4888	08168	$1-2^*(-3+4)+5678-9AB$	$B-A^* - 98^*7+6-(-5-43+21)$
4889	08169	$-1+2+3-4+5678-9AB$	$B-A9+8^*(765-(43-2))-1$
488A	08170	$-1+2+3^*45-6^*(78-9AB)$	$BA9-8-(-76-5^* - 43^* - 21)$
488B	08171	$1+2+3-4+5678-9AB$	$B-A-(-98^*7+6-(-5+4321))$
4890	08172	$1^*2-3-(-4-5678+9AB)$	$-B-A^*98+76+5432-1$
4891	08173	$1+2-3+4+5678-9AB$	$-B+A9-8-7^*6^* - 54^*3-2+1$
4892	08174	$1+2^{\wedge}3^*4^{\wedge}5+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A+987-65^*4^*(3-21)$
4893	08175	$-1234+567-8^* - 9^*AB$	$-BA9-87^*(-6-(-54-32))^* - 1$
4894	08176	$12-3-4+5678-9AB$	$BA-9-87^* - 65+4^*(3+21)$
4895	08177	$-1-(-2-3-4-5678)-9AB$	$-BA9-8+7^*(6-54^*(3-21))$
4896	08178	$12+34^* - 5^*6^* - 7-(89+AB)$	$B-A+987^*6+54^* - 3-21$
4897	08179	$1+2+3-(-4-(5678-9AB))$	$-B+A^*(-9-(8-76-543+21))$
4898	08180	$12+3+4-5+67^*89-AB$	$-B-A9^* - 8^*7+654+32+1$
4899	08181	$1^*(2+34+5-678)^*9^*(A-B)$	$B-A^*(9+87-654-3-2^* - 1)$
489A	08182	$12-(-3+4-5678+9AB)$	$BA+9-(8+7^*6^*54^* - 3)-21$
489B	08183	$-1^*(-2-3^*4-5678+9AB)$	$-B-(-A9-8^*765+432)-1$
489A	08184	$12-3+4+5678-9AB$	$-B+A^*98^*7-65+4^* - 32^* - 1$
48A1	08185	$-12-(-34-(-5+67^*89)+AB)$	$BA9-(-87+6)+5^*43^*21$
48A2	08186	$-1-234^* - 5+6^*789-AB$	$BA9-(-8-76)-5^*43^* - 21$
48A3	08187	$1^*2^{\wedge}3^*4^{\wedge}5+6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA9+8-7^*65^*4^* - 3+2^* - 1$
48A4	08188	$12+3-456+7^*(89A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-9-(87-654))+32+1$
48A5	08189	$-1+23+4-5-67^* - 89-AB$	$BA+9+876^*5-4^* - 321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
48A6	08190	$1*(-23-4+5)*(-67-89-AB)$	$-BA-9*87-(-6-5432+1)$
48A7	08191	$-1+23-4+5678-9AB$	$-B+A-98*7+6+5+4321$
48A8	08192	$-1*(-23-(-4+5678-9AB))$	$BA9-8-7*-654+3*(-2-1)$
48A9	08193	$1+23-4+5678-9AB$	$B+A-98*(7-65)-(-43-2+1)$
48AA	08194	$1+2*3*4-(-5678+9AB)$	$-BA-987*-6+(54-3*2)*-1$
48AB	08195	$-12-(-34-5)-67*-89-AB$	$B-A*98+76+5432*1$
48B0	08196	$-12+34*5+6*(-78+9AB)$	$-BA-(98-765-4321)$
48B1	08197	$-1+23-456+7*(89A-B)$	$BA9+87+6-5*43*21$
48B2	08198	$-123+45-(-67*89-A)+B$	$-B-A9*8-(7+6-5432)*1$
48B3	08199	$-1-(-23-4-5678+9AB)$	$B+A+98-7*6*-54*3+2*-1$
48B4	08200	$1*23+4+5678-9AB$	$B+A+98-7*6*54*-3-2+1$
48B5	08201	$1+23-(-4-5678)-9AB$	$BA9-(8+7*-654)-3+2+1$
48B6	08202	$-123-45+67*89+AB$	$-B+A9+8*76-(5-4321)$
48B7	08203	$-12-3+4*-567-8*-9AB$	$-BA+9-8*(-765+4+32+1)$
48B8	08204	$12*(345-6-7-8-9+AB)$	$BA9-8+7*654+3*(2-1)$
48B9	08205	$-1*(-2+3)*(-4*5-67*89-A*-B)$	$BA9-(8-7*(654-3))+21$
48BA	08206	$-1-2+34+5678-9AB$	$-BA-987*-6+5-43*(2-1)$
48BB	08207	$1*-2+34-(-5678+9AB)$	$B+A9-8*-765-432+1$
4900	08208	$1-2+34+5678-9AB$	$B-A*98*-7+65-(-4+3)-2+1$
4901	08209	$-1-23-456+7*89A-B$	$B+A+(9-(8-7)^6)^5/4-3-2+1$
4902	08210	$-1-2345*-6-7*-89*(-A-B)$	$-BA+987*6-(54-(-3+21))$
4903	08211	$-1-2-3+45-67*-89-AB$	$-B+A9*-8+7-6+5432-1$
4904	08212	$1+2-(-34-5678)-9AB$	$BA9+8-7*-654-3-2*1$
4905	08213	$12+34-(5+67*-89+AB)$	$-BA+9*(87+6)-(-5-4321)$
4906	08214	$-12-34-(-5+6)-(-78*9*A+B)$	$BA9-(-8+7*-65*-4*-3)+21$
4907	08215	$-12-345+678*9-A*-B$	$-B+A9+8+7*-6*54*-3+21$
4908	08216	$1+2+3-45-6+78*9*A-B$	$-BA-987*-6+5-(4+32)+1$
4909	08217	$1-(23+45+67*-89)-(-A-B)$	$BA9+8-7*-654-3+2+1$
490A	08218	$1+23+4-(5+6)-7*(8+9*-AB)$	$B+A9+8*765-432+1$
490B	08219	$-12+34*5+6*(78-9)*AB$	$B+A+(9-(8-7)^6)^5/4+3*2*1$
4910	08220	$1+2-3+4*-567-8*-9AB$	$-BA+9+8-7-654*3*(-2-1)$
4911	08221	$1+2345+6*7*89-AB$	$B+A+9+8*(765-4)-321$
4912	08222	$1-2+3-4*567+8*9AB$	$B+A9+8*765-(4*-32+1)$
4913	08223	$12-(-34-5678+9AB)$	$BA9-8-(7*-654-(-3+21))$
4914	08224	$-1234*(5-(-6-78+9A-B))$	$B+A9+8*765+43*(2+1)$
4915	08225	$-1-2*3*4-56*(7+8-9-AB)$	$-BA-9*(-8+7-654)-3*-2*1$
4916	08226	$-1-2-3-4*(-567-(89A-B))$	$B+A-9-(8+(7+6-5)^4+3)*-2*1$
4917	08227	$12+345+6*(7+89A+B)$	$BA-9+8*76-(-5-4321)$
4918	08228	$12-3+45+67*89-AB$	$-B*(-A+98-7-65)*(4-32*1)$
4919	08229	$1+2+34*-5+67*89+AB$	$-BA98-7+6*-54*3*-21$
491A	08230	$-1+2-(34+5)-67*-89-(A+B)$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6-5)^(4+3)/2*1$
491B	08231	$-1-23-456-7*-89A+B$	$BA+987*6-5+4*3*-21$
4920	08232	$1-(-2+345)+678*9+A*B$	$-BA+987*6+5*(4-3)-21$
4921	08233	$1-2*-3*(-4-56+7+8+9AB)$	$-BA-9-87*-65-4+321$
4922	08234	$123+45-6*(78-9AB)$	$BA+9-87*-65+4*-32*-1$
4923	08235	$-123+4*-5+67*89+AB$	$BA+9-8*-76-5+4321$
4924	08236	$-12-345+678*9+AB$	$BA*(9+8-7+6+5+4*3+21)$
4925	08237	$12+3-4*567-8*-9AB$	$BA-98*-7*(6+5-4+3)-21$
4926	08238	$12+3-45-67*-89-A-B$	$BA9-8-(-7*654-32+1)$
4927	08239	$1-23-(-4+5-67*89+A+B)$	$BA-9*876+543*21$
4928	08240	$1*-2*-34*(56-78+9A+B)$	$-BA+9*-8+765+4321$
4929	08241	$-1+234-5+6-7-8*9*-A*B$	$-BA-987*6+54-3*21$
492A	08242	$12-34+5-(6+78*9*-A+B)$	$-BA9-8*-765+43*21$
492B	08243	$1-(-2-3+456)-(-7*-89A+B)$	$-BA-987*-6-5-4+3-2-1$
4930	08244	$12+34-(-5-67*89-A*-B)$	$-BA+987*6+5-4*-3-21$
4931	08245	$-1-23+4-5+67*89-A-B$	$-B+A*9*(87-6-5)+4-3-21$
4932	08246	$-123-(-4+5-(-67*-89+AB))$	$BA-98*-7-(65-4321)$
4933	08247	$-12+34+5-67*(-89-A+B)$	$-BA+987*6*(5-4)-(-3+2*1)$
4934	08248	$-1-(2-34*(5-6)-78*-9*-A)+B$	$B-A-9*(-87+6)+5+4321$
4935	08249	$-123-45-678*-9-AB$	$-B-A+98-(7+6+5)*(4-321)$
4936	08250	$-123-(-4-5678)+9*-AB$	$B*(-A+9)*(-87+6+54+3)*21$
4937	08251	$1-234-5-(678*-9-(-A-B))$	$-B-A+9*(-87-6)+5432-1$
4938	08252	$-12-3-(-45+67*(-89-A+B))$	$-B-A+9+8*(765-43-2+1)$
4939	08253	$-1-2-3-(456+7*-89A-B)$	$B+A+9*8*7+6*5-(4+3)^2+1$
493A	08254	$-1234+5-67-8*9A*-B$	$-BA+98+76*(54+3+21)$
493B	08255	$-1-2-34+5678-9A*B$	$-B+A-9*(8+7-654)-(-32-1)$
4940	08256	$1*-2*-3*(456+7*89+A-B)$	$BA9-(-8-7*654-32-1)$
4941	08257	$-1-23-4-5+67*89+A-B$	$-B+A-98*-7+65+4321$
4942	08258	$-1-23-4-5-67*89*(A-B)$	$-B+A+987*6+(-54-3)*2-1$
4943	08259	$-1-23+4*(567+89A)+B$	$B-A+98*7+65+4321$
4944	08260	$1234+56*78-9A+AB$	$BA+9*(-8+76)*(-54-3*-21)$
4945	08261	$-1-2*-34*-5-(67-8)*(9-AB)$	$B-(-A-9-87*65)+4*3*21$
4946	08262	$1-(-2+34)+5-(-67*89-A+B)$	$-BA9+8*76+5432+1$
4947	08263	$-1-(-23+456)-(-7*89A+B)$	$-B+A98*7-65*(-4+32)*1$
4948	08264	$12-345-678*-9+AB$	$-B-A-9*-87-6-5+4321$
4949	08265	$1+23-456+7*89A-B$	$B+A*-9+8*(765-4-32)*1$
494A	08266	$12-34-5+6-78*9*-A+B$	$-B-A-(-987*6+5-43*-2*1)$
494B	08267	$-12-34+5+67*89-(-A-B)$	$-B-A-(9+87)-6*(5+43)*-21$
4950	08268	$1-23-4+5678+9A*-B$	$-BA+987*6+5-(-4-3*2-1)$
4951	08269	$-1+23-45-67*-89-A+B$	$-B+A-98-7*(65-43*21)$
4952	08270	$-123-(-45-678*9+A*B)$	$-BA+987*6+5-4*3+21$
4953	08271	$-1-(-2+3)+4-(5+67*-89)-(-A+B)$	$BA+987*6+5*(-43-2)*1$
4954	08272	$12-34+5678-9A*B$	$-B+A*-98*-7+6+5+4*-32*-1$
4955	08273	$1+2+3+4+56-7*(8+9*-AB)$	$B+A-9*-8*7+6*5-4*(3*2+1)$
4956	08274	$-1-23+4+5678+9A*-B$	$B-A9+8*765+4+321$
4957	08275	$-1-2-(3*4+5)-67*-89*(-A+B)$	$B+A+(9*-8+7)*(6-5-4^3*2)-1$
4958	08276	$-12-(-3+45)-6*(-78-9A*B)$	$BA9-8-7*-654+3*21$
4959	08277	$-12-3-4+5678+9A*-B$	$-B-A-987*-6+5+43*-2+1$
495A	08278	$1-23*-4+5678-9AB$	$B+A+9*-8*(7-65-(4+32+1))$
495B	08279	$1-2-(3-4)-(-5+67*-89+A+B)$	$-BA+987*6-(54-(-3+21))$
4960	08280	$1+2*-34*5+67*(-8+9A)-B$	$BA-(-9+8*(-76-5))+4321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4961	08281	-1-234+5+678*9-A+B	B-(A-9+8)-76*(5-43)*2-1
4962	08282	-1+2-34+5+67*89+A+B	-BA-9*-8*(-7-6)*(-5-4)-(-3+2)-1
4963	08283	1-234+5+678*9-(A-B)	-B*(-A9-(-8+765+4)+321)
4964	08284	-12+3-4+5-67*-89+A-B	-B+A+9*87-6-5+4321
4965	08285	1+2+3*-4*-567-8-9A*B	B+A-(-9+8*(-765-4))-321
4966	08286	12-(3+4)-(-5-67*89-(-A-B))	BA-987*-6-5*(43-2+1)
4967	08287	-12+34-5*6+78*-9*-A+B	-BA+9-8*76+5*-4*-321
4968	08288	12*(345-6+7+89-A+B)	B-A9*(-8+7-6)+5+4321
4969	08289	-1-(-23+45-67*89)+A+B	-B-A*-98-(-7+65)*-43*2*1
496A	08290	-12-345-(-67-8*-9*-A)*B	-BA-987*-6-(-5+4)-(-32+1)
496B	08291	-12+3-(-4-5678)-9A*B	-BA-987*6+5-4-32*-1
4970	08292	-1+2-3-4+5678-9A*B	BA9+8-7*-654-3*-21
4971	08293	-123-4-5+678*9-AB	B+A+9*8*7+6*5-4-3-2+1
4972	08294	1+234*56-(789A-B)	-BA+98*-7-6+5432*1
4973	08295	12-34+5-(-67*89-A-B)	-BA-(9+8-765)+4321
4974	08296	-1-(2+3-4-5678-9A*-B)	B-(A-9*87)-(6-5)+4321
4975	08297	-1-23-456-7*(-89A-B)	BA+98+7*6*54*3-21
4976	08298	-12-3*-4+5-67*-89*(-A+B)	-BA-98*7-6*-543*-2*-1
4977	08299	1-23-456-7*(-89A-B)	B+A*-987+6543*2*-1
4978	08300	1+2+3-(-4-5678)+9A*-B	-BA+9-8-(-7-6*54*(-3+21))
4979	08301	1+23*-4*(5+6)*-7-(8+9+A-B)	-B+A+987*6-54-(3+21)
497A	08302	-12-3-(-4-(-5*-67-8*-9*-A*-B))	-BA-987*-6-5*(-4+3*-2*1)
497B	08303	123-45-67*-89+A*-B	B+A+9*8*7+6*5-4+3*2/1
4980	08304	12-(-3+4+5-67*89)-A+B	-B-A-9*87-6*-543*2*1
4981	08305	12-(3+4-5678+9A*B)	B*(A9+8-7*-65+4+3*21)
4982	08306	1-(2-3*4*567)-(89A+B)	-B-A9-(8-(765+4321))
4983	08307	12-(3-4*-5-67*89)-(-A-B)	-B-A-(987*-6+54)-(-3-2+1)
4984	08308	1+234-(-56+7)-8*-9*A*B	BA-9+8*7*(-6-54-3)*-2-1
4985	08309	1*2+3+(4*5+6+7)*8+9+A-B	B-A+987*6-54-(-3+21)
4986	08310	-1+23-(-4+5+6-78*9-A-B)	-BA9-8*-7*(65-43*-2)-1
4987	08311	-1-23+4+56-78*-9*A-B	-BA+987*6+54+3*-2+1
4988	08312	-12+345-67-8*9*A*-B	BA+98*(-7+65)+43-2+1
4989	08313	12-3+4+5678+9A*-B	-BA-(-9+8)+765+4321
498A	08314	-12-(3+4-56-78*9*A+B)	B-A-987*-6-(5+43+21)
498B	08315	-12-3-456*(-7-8)+9A*-B	-B+A-9*(-8+7-654+(-3-2)*-1)
4990	08316	1*(2-34*5)*(67+8-9A-B)	-BA+9+8-7+6*54*(-3+21)
4991	08317	1-(2+3+45*(67-(89+AB)))	-B-A-(98-765)+4321
4992	08318	12-(3+4)-(5+67*-89-A-B)	-B-A-98+7+6*54*(-3+21)
4993	08319	-1-23+45-67*-89+A-B	B-(A-987*6)-(-5-4-3*-21)
4994	08320	-1*(23-45*67)*(-8+9-(A-B))	-B+A9*8+7-65+4321
4995	08321	1*23-4+5678-9A*B	-B+A9*-8*(-7-(6-5))+43+21
4996	08322	1+23-4+5678+9A*-B	-BA9-8-7+6*(54+3)*21
4997	08323	1-23+45+67*89-A+B	BA+98*7-(-6+5)*4321
4998	08324	-12-(-34-5678)-9A*B	BA-98*7+6-5+4321
4999	08325	-1-2+3-456-7*(-89A-B)	-B+A-987*-6-(54+3+2)+1
499A	08326	-1-23+4*-567-89*-A*B	B-A*(9-8-7*6*-5*-4)-3*21
499B	08327	1+2+3+45*(-67+89+AB)	-B-A*-9*87-654-3-2+1
49A0	08328	12-345*6+78*(-9+AB)	B-(A9+8-765)+4321
49A1	08329	1-2*3*-45+6*(-78+9AB)	-BA+9-(-8-(765+4321))
49A2	08330	-12*(-34+5)*(6-7+8+9-A+B)	B-A-9*(8-7*6)+(-5*-4)^3+2+1
49A3	08331	-1-(-2-3)+45-(67*-89+A+B)	-B-A+9*(8-7)*654-3+2+1
49A4	08332	-1+234-5-6*(78-9AB)	-B-A*-9-(8+7+6)*(54-321)
49A5	08333	-1+2+34-5+6+78*9*A+B	-BA+987*6+5-(-43-21)
49A6	08334	-1234+5-6+7-8*9A*-B	B-(A-9*-87-6)+5432*1
49A7	08335	-1-2+34+5678-9A*B	-B+A-987*-6-(5+43+2)*1
49A8	08336	123-4+5678-9AB	B+A98+7*(654+32+1)
49A9	08337	1-2+34-(-5678-9A*-B)	-B+A-98-(-765-4321)
49AA	08338	-1-2+3+45-6+78*-9*-A+B	B*(A9-(-8-(-7-(-6+5-4321))))
49AB	08339	-1+2*-3*-4*(5+67)*(-8+9-A)*-B	B-(A+98-765-4321)
49B0	08340	12-(-345+67)+8*-9*A*-B	-B-A-(98-7)*-65-(4+3+21)
49B1	08341	1+2+34+5678-9A*B	B+A-9*87-(6-5432+1)
49B2	08342	1*(-2+3+4+5)*(67+8+9A-B)	-BA+9*(8-7)^4(6-5)^4*3*2+1
49B3	08343	12+3*-4*-567-89A+B	-BA9+8+(-7-6)*-543+21
49B4	08344	123+4+5678-9AB	B-A9+8+765+4321
49B5	08345	12+3-(-45-6)-(-78*-9*-A+B)	-B+A*-9-8+765+4321
49B6	08346	1*2*3*(45+67+89A-B)	-B+A+9*(-8+7+654)+3-(-2+1)
49B7	08347	-1*(23-4*(567-(-89A-B)))	-B-A+987*6-54+32*1
49B8	08348	1+23-4*(-567-89A-B)	B+A+9*8-(-7-6)*(54+3^2+1)
49B9	08349	12-(3-45-(-6-(78*-9*A-B)))	-B+A+987*65+4*-3*-21
49BA	08350	-12+34*5-67*-89-AB	B-A+987*6-5*(-4-3-2)*-1
49BB	08351	1+2345-6*-7*89-(-A+B)	B+A+9*8*7+6*5+4(4+3)^2+1
4A00	08352	-12-3-(-45-67*89-A-B)	-B-A9+8+(7+65)*(43*2-1)
4A01	08353	1+23-456-7*(-89A-B)	B-A*-9*87-654-3+2+1
4A02	08354	1-2-34+(56+7)*(8+9A-B)	-B+A*-9*-87-654+3+2*-1
4A03	08355	123-4*-5+67*89-AB	B+A-9+8*(765-4-32)-1
4A04	08356	-12-3-45+67*89+AB	B-(A-987*6-5*-4)-(-32+1)
4A05	08357	-1-(2-(-34-5-67*-89-A*-B))	B+A+987*6-5*4+32*-1
4A06	08358	12*(345+6+7-8+9A-B)	BA+98-76*5*(4+3-21)
4A07	08359	-123-45-678*-9-A-B	B+A-98+765+4321
4A08	08360	1*(2-34)*(-5-(-6+78)-(9A+B))	-B*-A*(9+87-65+4-(-32+1))
4A09	08361	-12+34+56-78*9*-A-B	BA-9*-87-(65-4321)
4A0A	08362	-12-(345-6-7*(-89-A)*-B)	-B-A9-87*(-6-5)+4321
4A0B	08363	-1-2-3+45-(-67*89-A-B)	B+A+9*8*7+6*5+4^3*2*1
4A10	08364	-1*2*-3*(45-(-6+78-9AB))	-B-A+987*6+5+(-4-3)*-2*-1
4A11	08365	1-2-3+45-67*-89+A+B	B+A+9*8*7+6*5+4^3*(2-1)
4A12	08366	-1-(-2^3*(4^5+6+7)-8*9)+A-B	B+A-(987*-6-5)-(43+2)-1
4A13	08367	-1-(2+3)-(45+67*-89-AB)	BA9+8*-76-(-5-4321)
4A14	08368	1+2^3*(4^5+6+7)+8*9+A-B	B+A+9*8*7+6*5+4^3*2+1
4A15	08369	-1-2*-3*-4*-5+(-67*-8+9A)*B	-BA+9-87*(-6-5)+4321
4A16	08370	-1*2*(-3+45*-67-89+A*B)	B+A-98*(-7-65+4*3)-2-1
4A17	08371	-12+34*5+67*89+A*-B	-B*(-A9-8-(765-4)+321)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4A18	08372	$12^*(-3 -4 -5 +6 -7^* -89 -AB)$	$-B +A9^*8 - (7 +6 +5 -4321)$
4A19	08373	$1^*((2+3)^*4^*5+6)^*(7+8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9^*-8^*(-7 +6 -5 +4^*3)^* -2^*1$
4A1A	08374	$-1 -2 -34 +5678 +9^* -AB$	$B - (A +9^* -87 -65 -4321)$
4A1B	08375	$-1^*(-2 -3 +4 -56)^*(-7 -8 +9 +AB)$	$-B +A98 +7^* -65 +4321$
4A20	08376	$-123 +45 -678^* -9 -A^*B$	$-BA -9 +8^*765 +4^* -32 -1$
4A21	08377	$1 - (-23 -45) - (-67^*89 +A -B)$	$-BA -9 -8^* -765 -4^*32^*1$
4A22	08378	$-1 +2 -34 +5678 -9^*AB$	$BA^*(9 -8)^*(7 -65^*(-4 +3) -21)$
4A23	08379	$1 +2 +3 -45 -67^* -89 +AB$	$-B - (-A -987^*6 -5^*4) -3^* -2^*1$
4A24	08380	$-123 -45 -678^*9^*(A -B)$	$BA -987^* -6 -5 +4^* -32 +1$
4A25	08381	$-1 -234 - (-5 -67)^*89 +A^* -B$	$B - A +987^*6 -5^*4 +3 +2 +1$
4A26	08382	$1 - (-23 +4^*567) -89^*A^* -B$	$B^*(-A +98 -76 +543 -21)$
4A27	08383	$1^*2 +3^*(4 +5^*(6 +7^*8)^*9) +A -B$	$-BA -9 +8^* -76 +5432^*1$
4A28	08384	$12 -3 -45 -67^* -89 +AB$	$-B -A9 -8^* -765 -4^*(32 +1)$
4A29	08385	$-1^*2 + (-3^* -4^*(-5 -6)^* -7 +8)^*9 +A -B$	$B -A9 - (-87 +6^*(-5 -43))^*21$
4A2A	08386	$-12 - (345 - (6 -7^* -89A)) -B$	$BA9 -87 +65^*4^*(-3 +21)$
4A2B	08387	$-1 - (-23 -4) +56 - (78^* -9^*A -B)$	$-B -A9 +8^*765 +4^* -32 -1$
4A30	08388	$1 -23 +4 +5 +67^*89 +A^*B$	$-B -A9 +8^*765 +4^*32^* -1$
4A31	08389	$1 +2345^*6 - (7 +89AB)$	$BA -9^*(-87 +6) +5 +4321$
4A32	08390	$12 +3 -45 - (-67^*89 -AB)$	$-B -A^* -9^*87 - (-6 -5)^*(-4 +3^* -21)$
4A33	08391	$1^*234 +56 - (7 -8^* -9^*A)^* -B$	$-B -A98^* -7 +6 -54^*(32 +1)$
4A34	08392	$1 +2^* -3^* -4^*5^*(67 -8) -9A -B$	$-B +A9 +9 -87^* -65 -4 +321$
4A35	08393	$-1 - (23 -4 -5678) -9^*AB$	$-B^*(A9 -8 +7 -654 +32 -1)$
4A36	08394	$-123 +4 +5 -6^*(-7 +8 -9AB)$	$-BA -9 +87^*65 -432^* -1$
4A37	08395	$1 - (23 -4) - (-5678 +9^*AB)$	$B +A +987^*6 -5 -4 +3 -2 -1$
4A38	08396	$-123 +4567 +8^*(9A -B)$	$-B +A -9^*(8 -7 - (654 +3 +2) -1)$
4A39	08397	$-1 -2 -345 +6 +7^*89A -B$	$-B +A +987^*6 -5 +4 +3 -2^* -1$
4A3A	08398	$-12 +3^*4 -5 +67^*89 +A^*B$	$B +A -987^* -6 - (5^* -4 +32 -1)$
4A3B	08399	$-1 +2^*(-3 -45 -6 +78)^*(9 +AB)$	$-BA -9^*(8 -7 -654 +3 -21)$
4A40	08400	$123 +4 -56 +78^* -9^* -A +B$	$-B -A +987^*6 -5 +4 +3 +21$
4A41	08401	$-1 +23 -4 +5 -67^*(-89 +A -B)$	$-BA +9 +8^* -76 +5432^*1$
4A42	08402	$1^*2 -345 +6 +7^*89A -B$	$B +A +987^*6 -5 +4^*(-3 +2 -1)$
4A43	08403	$-12 -3 -45 +678^*9 -AB$	$B +A -9^*8 - (-765 -4321)$
4A44	08404	$-1 +23 -4 +56^*7 +8^* -9^*A^* -B$	$B^*(-A9 +87 -6 - (-543 -21))$
4A45	08405	$12 -3^* -4 +5 +67^*(89 -A +B)$	$-B -A9 +87^*65 +432^*1$
4A46	08406	$-12 +3 -4 -5 - (67^* -89 -AB)$	$-B -A^*9^* -87 -654 -3^* -21$
4A47	08407	$-1 -23 +4 - (-5 -67^*89 -AB)$	$BA +9^*(-8 -7) +6^*(-5 -43)^* -21$
4A48	08408	$-12 -345 +6 -7^* -89A +B$	$B +A9 +87^*(65 +4) -3^*21$
4A49	08409	$12 -34^* -5^*6^*7 +89 -A^*B$	$-BA -987^* -6 +5 +4^*32^*1$
4A4A	08410	$-12 +3 - (-4 -5678) +9^* -AB$	$-BA -987^* -6 +5 +4^*32 +1$
4A4B	08411	$-1 - (234 -5 -678^*9 -AB)$	$-BA - (-9 +87^* -65 -432 +1)$
4A50	08412	$1 +2 +3 +4^* -5 +67^*89 +AB$	$B - (-A -9) -87^*(-65 -4) - (-32 -1)$
4A51	08413	$-123 -4^*5 -678^*9^*(A -B)$	$B +A^* -98^* -7 +6^*(5 +4 +32)^*1$
4A52	08414	$12 -345 +6 -7^* -89A -B$	$-B +A -987^* -6 - (5 -43 +21)$
4A53	08415	$12 +3^* -4^* -567 - (8 +9^*AB)$	$B^*(-A -9 +876 -5 +4 -321)$
4A54	08416	$1 +23^* -4^*(-56 +7 -8) +9^*AB$	$-B -A - (9 +8) - (-765 -4321)$
4A55	08417	$1 +23 +4^* -5^* -6 -78^* -9^*A -B$	$B -A9 -8^*76 +5432 +1$
4A56	08418	$12 +34^* -5 +678^* -9^*(A -B)$	$-BA +9 - (-87 -6^* -54^*(3 -21))$
4A57	08419	$1 +2 - (-3 +4 -5678 -9^* -AB)$	$-B +A +987^*6 - (-54 +32) ^*1$
4A58	08420	$-1 +234^*(-56 +78) - (9A -B)$	$-B -A^* -98^*7 - (-6 -5) +4^*3^*21$
4A59	08421	$1 +2 -3 +4 +5678 +9^* -AB$	$BA -9 +8 -76^*(-54 -3 -21)$
4A5A	08422	$1234 +5^*(-6 +7 +89A) +B$	$B -A +987^*6 - (5 -4) - (-3 -21)$
4A5B	08423	$1 -2 - (3 +4 -5 +67^* -89 -AB)$	$-B -A -987^* -6 - (-5 +4 +3)^* -21$
4A60	08424	$-1 +2 - (-3 -4567 +8^*9^* -A) -B$	$-BA -9^*(-87 +6^* -5) +4321$
4A61	08425	$-1 +2 +3 - (-4 -5678) -9^*AB$	$B +A + (-9 +8 +7^*6 / (5 -4^*3)) / -2^*1$
4A62	08426	$-12 -34^*(5 - (67 - (8 -9A -B)))$	$-BA -9 - (8^* -765 +43^*2 +1)$
4A63	08427	$1 - (-2 -3) +4 +5678 -9^*AB$	$-BA +9^*8^*(76 -5 - (4 -32)) +1$
4A64	08428	$-1 +23^* -45^* -6 +7^* -8 +9 +A^* -B$	$-BA +98 +765 +4321$
4A65	08429	$1 -234^*5^* -6 - (-7 -8 +9AB)$	$B - (-A -9 +8 -7 +6^*(-5 -43))^*21$
4A66	08430	$123 -456 +7^*89A +B$	$B +A - (987^* -6 -5^*4) - (3 -2^* -1)$
4A67	08431	$1 +2 -34 -5 -678^* -9 -AB$	$BA +9^*(-8 +7 - (-654 +3) - (2 +1))$
4A68	08432	$-1 +23 -4 - (-5 +67^* -89 +A^* -B)$	$-B -A -9 +8 +765 +4321$
4A69	08433	$-1 +2^*345 -6^*(-789 -AB)$	$-B +A -987^* -6 +5^*(4 +3 +2 -1)$
4A6A	08434	$-1 +2 +3^*4 -5 +67^*89 +AB$	$BA +987^*6 -54 -32^*1$
4A6B	08435	$1 -2 + (3 +45 -6 +7)^*(8 - (-9 -AB))$	$-B - (-A +987^* -6 - (54 +3 -21))$
4A70	08436	$123 +4^*(567 +89A) -B$	$B - (A -98^* -7) - (6 - (5432 -1))$
4A71	08437	$1 -2 -34 +5 +678^*9 -AB$	$B +A9 -87 -6^*(-5 -43)^*21$
4A72	08438	$1234 -567^* -8 -9 - (-A +B)$	$B - (A +9 - (-8 +765) -4321)$
4A73	08439	$-1 - (-2 +34 -5 +678^* -9 +AB)$	$BA - (-9 -8) -76^*(-54 -3 -21)$
4A74	08440	$123 +45 +67^*(89 +A -B)$	$B -A -987^* -6 +5^*(4 +3 -2^* -1)$
4A75	08441	$1 +23 -4 +5678 -9^*AB$	$B +A +987^*6 + (-54 +32) ^* -1$
4A76	08442	$-12 -3^*4 -5 - (-678^*9 +AB)$	$BA +9^* -8^*(-7 -6) - (5 -4321)$
4A77	08443	$-12 +34 +5678 -9^*AB$	$-B -A98^* -7 -6 -54^*32^*1$
4A78	08444	$-1 -23 + (4 -5)^*6^*(7 +8 -9AB)$	$-B +A^* -98^* -7 -6^*5^* -4^*3 -21$
4A79	08445	$123 -4^*5 -67^* -89 - (-A +B)$	$-B +9 -8^* -765 +43^*2^* -1$
4A7A	08446	$123 +4^* -5 +67^* -89^*(A -B)$	$B +A +9^*8^*7 +6^*5 + (4^*3) ^2 +1$
4A7B	08447	$-12 - (-34 +5 -67^*89 -AB)$	$-B -A +987^*6 - (5 -4) +3^*21$
4A80	08448	$1 +2 - (-3 -4567) -8^*9^* -A +B$	$-B^*(-A - (-9 +8 +7) - (6 +543) +21)$
4A81	08449	$-1 -234 +56^*(7 +89 +A +B)$	$B +A + (-9^*(-8 +7^*6) +5^* -4^*(3^*2 +1))$
4A82	08450	$-1 +2 + (-3 -4)^*(-5 +67 -89A -B)$	$-B -A - (-9 -8 -765) +4321$
4A83	08451	$-1 +23 -4^* -5 +67^*89 -A^* -B$	$B +A +9^*8^*(7 +6)^*(5 +4) +3^*2^*1$
4A84	08452	$-1234 -56 +7^* -8^* -9^*(A +B)$	$-B +A -9 - (-8 -765 -4321)$
4A85	08453	$1 - (-23 -4) -5 - (67^* -89 -AB)$	$B -A - (-987^*6 -54) -3 -2 -1$
4A86	08454	$123 +4 +5 - (-67^*89 - (-A -B))$	$-B +A9 -8 +765 +4321$
4A87	08455	$123 +4 +5 +6 - (78^* -9^*A +B)$	$BA +9 +87^*(65 +4) - (32 +1)$
4A88	08456	$123 -4 -5 +67^*89 +A -B$	$B - (A - (9 -8 +765) -4321)$
4A89	08457	$12 +3^*4 +5 +67^*89 +AB$	$-B +A^*9^*87 -6 -543 -21$
4A8A	08458	$1 +2^* -3 - (4 +5) +6^*(-7 -8 +9AB)$	$B +A -9 -8 +765 +4321$
4A8B	08459	$1234 -567^* -8^*(-9 +A) +B$	$BA9 +87^* -6 - (5 -4321)$
4A90	08460	$-12 -34 + (5 -67 +8)^*(-9A -B)$	$-B -A9^* -8 -7 +65 +4321$
4A91	08461	$1 -2^* -3^*(45 -6)^*(-78 - (9 -AB))$	$-B +A9 -87^*(-6^*(5 -4) -3^*21)$
4A92	08462	$1 +2 -34 +5 -678^* -9 -A^*B$	$B +A + (9 + (8 - (7 -6))^5 +4^*3) / 2 +1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4A93	08463	$(1-2+3)^4 \cdot (-5)^{-6} \cdot 8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9 \cdot 8^*(7+(6^5/4+3)^2)^{11}$
4A94	08464	$1+2-(-3+4+5-6+7+8+9)+AB$	$-B+A98+76^5-5+4321$
4A95	08465	$-12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9-A-B$	$-BA-9+876+5+4321$
4A96	08466	$123+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9+876-5+4321$
4A97	08467	$123-4-(-5-6+7-8+9-(A-B))$	$-BA+98^*(7+6+5+4-3)+21$
4A98	08468	$1+2-3+4+5+6+7-8+9A^*-B$	$B+A+(-9+8+(-7-6)^5)^{-4} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 2-1$
4A99	08469	$1^*23+4+5+6+7-8+9^*-A+B$	$BA9+87^*-6+5+4321$
4A9A	08470	$-1^*2^*(3-4)^5 \cdot ((-6+7)^*-8+9A+B)$	$-B^*(A98-7-6-5+4-3)^2 \cdot -1$
4A9B	08471	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+8^*-7^*-6^*5^*4-3^2 \cdot -1$
4AA0	08472	$-1+2+3^*-45^*-6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B-A+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4AA1	08473	$123+4-(-5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-BA-(-9-8+7-6-5+4+3+2+1)$
4AA2	08474	$-12+3-4-5-6+7+8+9+A^*-B$	$BA9-8-7-6+5+4^*(3-2+1)$
4AA3	08475	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9-A^*-B$	$-B-A+9+8+7+6+5+4-3+2-1$
4AA4	08476	$123-(-4-5-6+7+8+9)-A+B$	$-B-A9+876+5+4321$
4AA5	08477	$-1+2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2^*-1$
4AA6	08478	$1-(2+3)-(-4-5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A9+8+7+6^*5^*4^*(3-2+1)$
4AA7	08479	$1+2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8-7)+6)^{-5} \cdot -4^*3^2 \cdot 2^*1$
4AA8	08480	$-1+2-3-(-4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$BA-98-(-765-4321)$
4AA9	08481	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A^*98-7^*6-(-5-4+3+2+1)$
4AAA	08482	$1-(-2-3^*(4+5+6))-(-7+8^*-9+A+B)$	$-B-A9^*-8+7+6-5+4^*3^*2+1$
4AAB	08483	$-1-(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$BA+9^*(-8+7+6+5+4-3)+21$
4AB0	08484	$-1-(-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$B-(-A9-8^*(7+6+5+4+3+2+1))$
4AB1	08485	$12-3-4-(-5+6+7+8+9)-AB$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4AB2	08486	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9-A-B$	$-BA-(9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4AB3	08487	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+A^*-B$	$B-A+(9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)-1$
4AB4	08488	$1-(-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9)-AB$	$B-(A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4AB5	08489	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4AB6	08490	$12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4AB7	08491	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+A^*B$	$B-A9-(8^*-7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4AB8	08492	$-1^*(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)^*B$	$-BA-9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4AB9	08493	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9^*-A+B$	$-BA+9+8^*(7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4ABA	08494	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A-9^*(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4ABB	08495	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9-8^*-7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B00	08496	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B01	08497	$-1^*(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-BA+9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B02	08498	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-(A9-(8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)-4321)$
4B03	08499	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B04	08500	$1+(2+3)^4 \cdot 5^*(6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2^*1$
4B05	08501	$-1+2^*(3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-BA+9^*-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B06	08502	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B07	08503	$12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B^*(-A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B08	08504	$1-2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B09	08505	$1^*2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B0A	08506	$-1^*(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B0B	08507	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9-8^*(-7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B10	08508	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B11	08509	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B12	08510	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B13	08511	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B14	08512	$12^*(3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-B+A-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B15	08513	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9-8^*(7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B16	08514	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B17	08515	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A^*-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B18	08516	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B19	08517	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A^*-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B1A	08518	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B1B	08519	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-A9-8^*(-7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B20	08520	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA^*(9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B21	08521	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B22	08522	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+8^*(7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B23	08523	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B24	08524	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B25	08525	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B26	08526	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B27	08527	$12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-A^*9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B28	08528	$-1^*2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A+(-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B29	08529	$1+2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B2A	08530	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9-8^*(7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B2B	08531	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B30	08532	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B31	08533	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B32	08534	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B+A-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B33	08535	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B34	08536	$123-4-5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B35	08537	$-12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-(A9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)+21$
4B36	08538	$-12-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B37	08539	$-1-(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B38	08540	$-12-(-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$B+A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B39	08541	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B-A^*-9-(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B3A	08542	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B3B	08543	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B40	08544	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B+A-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B41	08545	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-A^*-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B42	08546	$1-(2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-B+A9+(-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B43	08547	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-B^*(-A+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$
4B44	08548	$1-2-3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA-(-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)-1$
4B45	08549	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B46	08550	$12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-A^*9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B47	08551	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B48	08552	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$B-A9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$
4B49	08553	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB$	$BA-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
4B4A	08554	-1+2+3-45-678*-9+A-B	-B+A-(-9-(87*65-(-432-1)))
4B4B	08555	1234-567*-8+9A-B	-BA-9+8*765+4-(3-21)
4B50	08556	-1-(-2-3)-(45-678*9-(-A+B))	B-A+9-87*-65+432+1
4B51	08557	1-23-45*6-7*-89A+B	B-A*-9-8*-7+6*(-5-43)*-21
4B52	08558	12-3*-4*-5-678*9*(-A+B)	B-A9+8*765-4-3+2+1
4B53	08559	-12-3-4+5*(-6-7)*(8-9-AB)	-B+A*98*7-6-5+4+321
4B54	08560	-1+2345+6*-7*(8-9)*A*B	B+A+((9*8+7)*6*(5+4)+3)*2+1
4B55	08561	-1234-567-8*-9AB	BA+987*6+(-5-(4+3))*-2+1
4B56	08562	-1-(-23-4*56*-7)-8*-9A*B	BA+987*6+54+32*-1
4B57	08563	-1-2-34-(-5678+9*A*B)	-B+A-98+765*4*(3-2+1)
4B58	08564	12+3+45+678*9-A*B	-B+A*9*(-8+7*6-(-54+3))+21
4B59	08565	1-(2+34-5678-9*A*-B)	BA9*(87-6-54-3-21)
4B5A	08566	1*-2-34+5-(-678*9-A)-B	-B-(A-9-8*765)-43*-2*-1
4B5B	08567	123-4-5+67*89-A*-B	B-A*9-8*-765+4-32*1
4B60	08568	12*(3+4-5+6-7*-89-AB)	B+A+9*87+6*(-5-43*-21)
4B61	08569	-123+4-(-5-67)*(89-(-A+B))	-B-(-A-98)-(-765-4321)
4B62	08570	1234-567*-8-9+AB	-B-A*9+8*765-(4+3+2)*1
4B63	08571	1+(2+3)*(4+5*6*7)*8+9-(A-B)	B-A+98+765+4321
4B64	08572	-12-3*45*(-6+78-9-AB)	BA+987*6-5+4+32-1
4B65	08573	-12+3-4+5-(678*9-(-A-B))	-BA+9-8*-765+43-21
4B66	08574	1*2*-3*(-4-5+6-7+8-9AB)	BA-987*-6-(-5-(-4+32)+1)
4B67	08575	12+3-45-67*(-8+9-A*B)	B+A+(-9-8*-7)*(6+5*-4)*(3*-2-1)
4B68	08576	-1+23*-45*6*(7-8)+9*(A-B)	-B-(A+9)+876-(5-4321)
4B69	08577	1234-567*-8+9A+B	B-A*-98-(-7+6*-5)+4321
4B6A	08578	12-3+4567-8*(-9A+B)	-BA-9-8*-765+43+2*-1
4B6B	08579	-12-34-567+8*-9*-AB	BA-9-8+765+4321
4B70	08580	12-34+5678+9*A*-B	-B+A9+8+765+4321
4B71	08581	-1-(-23-456+7)-8*9*-A*B	-BA-9-8*-765+43+2-1
4B72	08582	12-34+5+678*9+A-B	B+A-(-987*6-54*3+21)
4B73	08583	1-(-2+3)-(45*6+7*-89A)+B	-B+A*9+8*(76*5+432-1)
4B74	08584	1-2*-3+(4+5)*(-6-78*-9+AB)	-B-A+(9+8*(7*6*5+4))*(3+2*1)
4B75	08585	-12-3-4+5678+9*A*-B	B+A+9-(-8*-7+6)*(-5-4^3)*2-1
4B76	08586	-12-3+4*5-(-678*9A)-B	-B-A-(9-876-5-4321)
4B77	08587	-1-23+45+6*(-7+8)*9AB	B+A9-(8-(7+6*-54*(3-21)))
4B78	08588	-12+3-45+6*(7+8+9AB)	-BA+9-8*-765-(-4-32+1)
4B79	08589	1*-23-4-5+678*9+A+B	B+A*-9*-87-(65+432+1)
4B7A	08590	(1+2*3*4*5)*(6+7*8+9)+A-B	-B-A9-8*-765+43-2+1
4B7B	08591	123+4567+8*9*A-B	B+A-(-98-(765+4321))
4B80	08592	-1*2*-3*(45*6-(-789-(-A+B)))	-B-A+9-8*-765-43-21
4B81	08593	-1+2-3-4-5-678*-9*(-A+B)	-B-A-9+8+7-6^5+4^4*(3*2+1)
4B82	08594	12-3-45*6+7*89A+B	BA+987*6+54-3-2-1
4B83	08595	-1-234*5*6*(789+AB)	BA-9+8+765+4321
4B84	08596	-1*(-23-456-7-8*-9*-A*B)	-B+A-9+876-5+4321
4B85	08597	1+234*5*6-789-AB	BA+9-8+765+4321
4B86	08598	123-(4-5-(67*89+AB))	B-(A+9-876+5-4321)
4B87	08599	-12-(3+4)-(5+678*-9-A-B)	-B+A*(987-65-(4+321))
4B88	08600	12-(-3-45*6)-7*-89A+B	BA-9*-8+7*(-65+43*21)
4B89	08601	1+23*4+(56+78*-9-A)*-B	-B+A*9+87*-6+5*-4*-321
4B8A	08602	-12-(-3-4)-(-5+678*-9*(-A+B))	B+A9+8-(-765-4321)
4B8B	08603	-12-34+5+6*(7+8+9AB)	-B-A-987*6-5*43-21
4B90	08604	-1+23*-45*-6-7-89+AB	-BA+9*876-54*-32*-1
4B91	08605	-12+3-4-5-678*-9+A+B	B+A*-9+8*765+4+3-2-1
4B92	08606	-12+34-5*6*(78-9A)*B	-B+A-9+876+5+4321
4B93	08607	12-34-567-8*-9*AB	BA-987*6-5+43+21
4B94	08608	-1+2-3+4+5678+9*A*-B	B+A+9-8*-765-43*2*1
4B95	08609	-1-23+4-567+8*9*AB	-B-A*(987+65-432)*-1
4B96	08610	-12*3*(-4-5*6-78+9*-A+B)	-B+A-987*6-54*-3+21
4B97	08611	1+2-34-(5+678)*-9+A-B	-B-A*9-8*-765+4-(-3-21)
4B98	08612	-1-2*3*-45+67*89*(-A+B)	BA9-8+7-6*(-5+43)*-21
4B99	08613	12-(3-4)-(5-(-678*-9+A-B))	BA-(-9-(8+765+4321))
4B9A	08614	-1*2*(-345+678+9AB)	-B+A+9+876-5+4321
4B9B	08615	-12-345+6*(78+9AB)	-BA+987-6-5+4321
4BA0	08616	-1+2+3+4+5+678*9+A-B	B-A-(-9-(876-5)))+4321
4BA1	08617	123-4*-5-67*-89+AB	-B+A+9-(-8*765-4)-3*21
4BA2	08618	1-23+4567+8*9A-B	B+A-(9-876+5-4321)
4BA3	08619	1234-5+6*789A*-B	B-A-(-9-8*765-4)-3*21
4BA4	08620	1-(-234+5)-(-67*89+A-B)	B+A9*8*7+654+321
4BA5	08621	-1-(23+45*6+7*(-89A-B))	BA+98*7*(6+5)+4-321
4BA6	08622	12+3-4+5+678*-9*(A-B)	B+A+9-8*-765-4*(-3+21)
4BA7	08623	-12+3+4+5-678*-9-(-A-B)	-B+A-9+8+(76+5*43)*21
4BA8	08624	-1*2*(-3-45)*(67-(-8+9))-(-A+B))	-B-(A-9)-(-87*-6+5432*-1)
4BA9	08625	-12-345-(6+(-78+9)*-A*-B)	-BA+987-6-(-5-4321)
4BAA	08626	1*234-(-5678-9A*-B)	-BA+987+6(6-5)*4321
4BAB	08627	1+234-(-5678+9A*B)	-BA+987-(-6+5-4321)
4BB0	08628	-123+4*-5+6+7*(89A-B)	B+A-(9-876-5-4321)
4BB1	08629	1-234-5-6+7*(89A+B)	-B+A9+8*(76*5+432)-1
4BB2	08630	-1+2-(345+6*(-78-9AB))	-BA-9-8*-765-43*-2-1
4BB3	08631	12+3+4+5-678*-9-A+B	B+A+(-98-7)*(-6-54)-3+2+1
4BB4	08632	1+23+4-5-678*-9-(-A-B)	-B-A-9+8*765+4-(-3+21)
4BB5	08633	-1+2-(-3-(-4-567)+8*-9*AB)	B-A9+8*(765+4)+32+1
4BB6	08634	-12-(-34-(5+678*9))-(-A+B)	-B-A-(-9+8*-765-4-32*-1)
4BB7	08635	-12-(-345-67*89)-AB	B*(-A+9+876+5-4-321)
4BB8	08636	123-4+5-6-7*(8-9A)*B	B+A+9+876-5+4321
4BB9	08637	-12-(-3+45)-(-67*(8-9A)-B)	-BA+987+6-(-5-4321)
4BBA	08638	-1-(-234+5+67*-89-A)+B	-B-A9*-87-6*(543-2*-1)
4BBB	08639	-1*(234-56-7*89A-B)	B-A+9+8*765+43*(-2+1)
5000	08640	-1*2*-3*(45-6-(-7+(-8-9A)*B))	-BA-9*-87-65*43*-2+1
5001	08641	-1+2+3+4-567+8*9*AB	BA+987*6+5*(4+3)*(2+1)
5002	08642	-1+2*345-6*(-7-89A)+B	-BA98-7*6-54*-321
5003	08643	1-(-23-45+6*(-7+8)*-9AB)	-B-A-(-9+8*(-765+4))+3*2+1
5004	08644	1*-2+34-(-5678-9*A*-B)	B+A-9+8*765-43+2+1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5005	08645	$-12+3+45-678^*-9-(-A+B)$	$-BA+987^*6-54+321$
5006	08646	$1-2+3+4567-(-8^*9A+B)$	$B+A-(-9-876-5-4321)$
5007	08647	$-1+2+34+5678+9^*-A^*B$	$-B-A^*-98^*7+65+4+321$
5008	08648	$1-2+345+67^*89-AB$	$B-A+9+8^*765-4+32^*-1$
5009	08649	$-12-3+4567+8^*9A+B$	$-BA+9-8^*-765+43^*2^*1$
500A	08650	$1+234-(-5+67^*-89)-(-A-B)$	$-B+A-987^*-6+5^*43-2^*-1$
500B	08651	$-1-2^*3+45-(-678^*9-(-A+B))$	$B+A+9+8^*(765-4)-3^*(2+1)$
5010	08652	$1+2-(-345+67^*-89+AB)$	$-B-A9^*8+7^*(654+321)$
5011	08653	$123+456-7^*8^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A-(-9^*87^*6-5^*-432^*-1)$
5012	08654	$12+3-45+67^*(-8+9)^*A^*B$	$BA+9+87-6^*(-5-43)^*21$
5013	08655	$-12+3+4567-8^*-9A+B$	$B+A+(-9-87)^*.65+4+3+2+1$
5014	08656	$1+2-(3-45)+678^*9-(-A+B)$	$B+A-9-(-8^*765-4^*3^*(-2-1))$
5015	08657	$-123+4-(-5-6)+7^*(89A-B)$	$-B^*(-A-(-98-7)-(654-3-21))$
5016	08658	$1^*2^*-3^*(-4-5-(-6-7+8+9AB))$	$BA9-8-(-7^*654-321)$
5017	08659	$-1-23+4567-8^*(9-AB)$	$B-A-(9-8^*765+4^*3)-2+1$
5018	08660	$-123+4567-8^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6)^*5^*4^*3^*2-1$
5019	08661	$12+3^*4^*-56+7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A9-87-65^*4^*(-3-21)$
501A	08662	$1^*(2-(-34-(-5-6^*-7))-8)^*(-9+AB)$	$B+A+9-8^*-765-43-(-2-1)$
501B	08663	$12+345+67^*89-AB$	$-B+A9-87^*.65+432^*1$
5020	08664	$1+234-5+6^*(78-9A^*-B)$	$B-(A-9)+8^*765-(4-(-3-21))$
5021	08665	$-12-(34-567)+8^*9^*A^*B$	$B-A+9+8^*765-(-4+3)^*-21$
5022	08666	$12+3+45^*-6+7^*(89A+B)$	$B-(-A-9)-87^*6+5432^*1$
5023	08667	$-1^*23^*(4-5^*-6^*-7-8-9A+B)$	$B-(-A+9)-(-8^*(765-4)-3^*2-1)$
5024	08668	$-123-(-4+56)-7^*-89A+B$	$BA-9^*-8-(-765-4321)$
5025	08669	$-1+2^*3^*(-45-(-67+8-9AB))$	$B-A^*-9^*87+6^*(-54-32)^*1$
5026	08670	$-1+2+3+4567+8^*9A+B$	$-B-(A+9)-(8^*765-4^*(-3-2)^*-1)$
5027	08671	$-123-45-6+7^*89A+B$	$B-(A+9+8^*-765^*(-4+3)+2-1)$
5028	08672	$12-3-45-678^*-9-A^*-B$	$B+A-987-6^*(54+3)^*-21$
5029	08673	$-12-3-(45-67+89)^*-A^*B$	$-BA-9-8^*(-765+4+3-21)$
502A	08674	$-1+2-(-34+567-8^*-9^*-AB)$	$-B-(-A+9+8^*-765-4)-(-3+2+1)$
502B	08675	$-1-(23-4^*-56-7^*(89A+B))$	$B+A9-(-8^*-76-5432-1)$
5030	08676	$-1+23-456+78^*(-9-A^*-B)$	$BA-987^*-6+5^*-4^*(-3^*2-1)$
5031	08677	$1-23-4^*56-7^*(-89A-B)$	$B-(-A-9-8^*765-4+32-1)$
5032	08678	$1+2-3+45+678^*9A+B$	$BA-9+87^*65+432^*1$
5033	08679	$1-23-4-5+678^*9-A^*-B$	$B^*(A9-87-6+543-2^*1)$
5034	08680	$-1+2-3-45-678^*-9+AB$	$B+A+9+(8-7-6^*5-4^*3)^2+1$
5035	08681	$-1-(23-4567+8+9^*-A^*B)$	$B-A+9+8^*765+4+3^*2-1$
5036	08682	$-1-(2+3-4)-(-5-(67^*(-8+9A)-B))$	$-BA+987^*6-5+4^*32-1$
5037	08683	$12+3+4567-8^*-9A+B$	$BA98-7+6+54^*321$
5038	08684	$12+345+67^*89-A^*B$	$B+A9-87^*-65+432-1$
5039	08685	$123-4^*(-5-6)+7^*(8-9A)^*-B$	$-BA98+7-6-54^*-321$
503A	08686	$1234+5^*-6^*(-78-9A-B)$	$B+A9-87^*-65+432+1$
503B	08687	$1+23^*45^*6+78-(-9-(A-B))$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6)^*(5^*4^*3^*2)^1$
5040	08688	$1-2-(3+4+5-67^*(-8+9A)-B)$	$B-(-A+98^*-7+65^*43^*-2)+1$
5041	08689	$-1-2-34-(-56+7)^*(8+9+AB)$	$-B-A^*(-98-7^*-6-543-21)$
5042	08690	$-12+3+(45-(6+7^*9A))^*-B$	$-B+A+987-(65-4321)$
5043	08691	$-1-2^*(34-5+6)^*(7+8-9A+B)$	$-BA+9+8^*(765-4-3+21)$
5044	08692	$-1^*(23-4-(-56+7))^*(-89+A-B)$	$B-A+987-65+4321$
5045	08693	$-123-4-5-(6-7^*89A)-B$	$B+A-9-8^*-765-4-(-3-2^*1)$
5046	08694	$1-(2-3-(-4-5))+67^*(-8+9A)+B$	$B+A+9+87^*6^*5+4^*(3^*2+1)$
5047	08695	$-1234-567-89^*A^*-B$	$BA+9-(87^*-65-432+1)$
5048	08696	$1+2^*(3-4+5)^6+7^*8^*9A-B$	$B-A+9+8^*(765+4-3)+2^*-1$
5049	08697	$-1+23^*-45^*-6-7^*(-8-(9+A-B))$	$-BA98+7+6+54^*321$
504A	08698	$1+2-34^*5-(6+7^*-89A)+B$	$B+A-9-8^*-765+4-(-3+2)+1$
504B	08699	$12+3^*45-6^*7^*(8^*-9-AB)$	$-BA-(-9-8^*765)+4^*.32^*-1$
5050	08700	$1^*(-2-3-45)^*(-67+8^*-9-A+B)$	$-BA+9+8^*765+43^*(2+1)$
5051	08701	$-123+45+6+7^*(89A-B)$	$-B^*(A-98+7-65-432-1)$
5052	08702	$1-234-(-567-89)^*A-B$	$-B-(-A+9)-8^*(-765-4)+3-(2+1)$
5053	08703	$-1-2-3+4567-(-8-9^*-A^*-B)$	$-BA+987-(-65-4321)$
5054	08704	$12+3+4567-8^*(9-AB)$	$-B+A987^*-6^*5+4321$
5055	08705	$(-1-2)^*-3/4^*-5-(6-7^*-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-(-9-8^*765)-4-(-3+2)^*-1$
5056	08706	$-1-(-23+4-5)-(67^*(8-9A)+B)$	$-B+A-9+8^*(765+4)+3+2-1$
5057	08707	$123+4^*(5+67-(8-9A))^*B$	$B+A-9^*(8-7^*(6+5+4^*3^*2))+1$
5058	08708	$12^*(-345-6-7+8^*(9+AB))$	$-BA+987^*6-5+4+321$
5059	08709	$(-1^*2^*(3^*4-5)-6)^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-B-A^*(-98+7)^*(-6-5+4-3+2)^*-1$
505A	08710	$1-234+5^*-67-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B+A98^*(7-(6-5))-432-1$
505B	08711	$-123+4567-8+9^*AB$	$B+A+9+8^*765-4-3^*-2-1$
5060	08712	$-123+4+56-7^*(-89A+B)$	$BA-(-98-765)+4321$
5061	08713	$-1-(-23-4567)-8^*(9-AB)$	$-B+A-(987^*-6+54^*(-3+2^*-1))$
5062	08714	$1+23+(4+5)^*(678+9)-A+B$	$-B+A^*9-87^*6+5432-1$
5063	08715	$1+2^*-34^*5+6^*(78+9AB)$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7^*6+5^*4+3+2)^1$
5064	08716	$-1-(23-4-(5-678^*-9)-AB)$	$B-(-A+9-8^*765+4-3-21)$
5065	08717	$-12-3+4-5-678^*-9+AB$	$-B-A+987-6^*5+4321$
5066	08718	$123+45-678^*-9-A^*B$	$B-(-A+9)+8^*765+43-21$
5067	08719	$-1234+5678+9^*AB$	$-B+A-(9+8^*-765)-(-43-2)^*-1$
5068	08720	$1-23^*45^*-6+7-(-89-A-B)$	$B-A^*(-98-7-6-5)+4321$
5069	08721	$123^*(4+56-(-7-(89-AB)))$	$B-A^*(-9+87-(654-(-32+1)))$
506A	08722	$123-45-678^*-9^*(-A+B)$	$-B-(-A+9-8^*765)-(-43-2+1)$
506B	08723	$1+2-(3-4-567+8^*-9^*-A^*-B)$	$-B^*(A9-87-6-(-543-2))^*-1$
5070	08724	$1-23+4567+89^*A-B$	$-B+A+9+76-(5-4321)$
5071	08725	$-123-4+5-6+7^*89A+B$	$-B-(-A-98)+7^*-6^*-5^*(4+32-1)$
5072	08726	$12+3+4567+8-9^*-A^*B$	$-BA98+7^*6+54^*321$
5073	08727	$1-2-(3^*4-(5-678^*-9+AB))$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+(6-5)^4)^3+2^*1$
5074	08728	$1234-5-6^*-789A+B$	$BA9+8+7^*65^*(-4^*3+21)$
5075	08729	$-1+23-4^*56-7^*(-89A-B)$	$B+A-9^*8-7+(6+5^*4)^3/2-1$
5076	08730	$-1+2+34+(-5-67)^*-89-AB$	$BA+987^*6+54^*3+2^*1$
5077	08731	$-1-2-34-(-5-(67+8))^*(9A-B)$	$-BA+9^*876-5^*(4+321)$
5078	08732	$1234-56^*(-78-9)^*(-A+B)$	$BA-9+8^*(765-4-3)-21$
5079	08733	$1234+5-6^*(-789-A+B)$	$-B-A^*-9+8^*765-(43-21)$
507A	08734	$-12-3+4-56-7^*(-89A+B)$	$B^*(A-9+87+65+432-1)$
507B	08735	$-1-(-23-4567-8+9^*-A^*B)$	$-B-A^*-98^*7-(-6-5-432-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5080	08736	$1-2+3+4-5+678^9+AB$	$-B+A-(-9+8^*-765-43-(-2-1))$
5081	08737	$-1+234+5+67^8+9+A^*B$	$BA-(9+8^*-765+43+21)$
5082	08738	$123+4567+8^*(9A-B)$	$B+A9^*87+6^*-5^*-4^*32^*-1$
5083	08739	$-12-3+4567+(-89+A)^*-B$	$BA-9+876-5+4321$
5084	08740	$1+23+(4+5+67)^*(-8+9A-B)$	$B-A+9-8^*-765-(-43+2)+1$
5085	08741	$-1-(-23-45+(67-8)^*(9-AB))$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6^*5^*4/3)^2-1$
5086	08742	$-123+4-5^*-6-7^*-89A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6^*5^*4/3)^2+1$
5087	08743	$12-(-3+4)-5-678^*-9+AB$	$BA-(-9+8^*-765)+4^*(3-21)$
5088	08744	$-12-345^*(-6-7-8)-9AB$	$-B-A^*(-9-8-76-543)-21$
5089	08745	$-1^*(-234-5678+9^*AB)$	$B-A^*98^*-7-6+5+432+1$
508A	08746	$1+234+5678+9^*-AB$	$B+A9+876-5+4321$
508B	08747	$-1-2^*-34+(567+8-9-A)^*B$	$-B+A9+8^*765-43^*(2-1)$
5090	08748	$-1^*23^*(4-5-(67+89+AB))$	$BA-(A-987-6)-5+4321$
5091	08749	$1^*2^3+4^5+(6+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA-9+876+5+4321$
5092	08750	$1+2-3+4567-(-89^*A+B)$	$-B+A9+8^*765-(-43-(2+1))$
5093	08751	$1-(2+3-4^*5)-(-678^*9-AB)$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7^*6+5^*4+3^*2)^1$
5094	08752	$1-(234-5-67^*(89+A)+B)$	$B+A+9^*(-8+7-(-6^*5/4+3))/2+1$
5095	08753	$-1+2^*3+4-5+67^*(-8+9A)-B$	$-B+A9+87^*-6-(-5432+1)$
5096	08754	$12-34+(5+678)^*9+AB$	$B+A^*9^*87-(6+54)-321$
5097	08755	$-1-2^*(-3+45)^*-67+8^*(9A-B)$	$-B+A-9^*8^*7-(6+5432)^*-1$
5098	08756	$12-3^*-45+678^*9-A-B$	$B+A9-(-876-5)+4321$
5099	08757	$1-23-456-7-8^*-9^*AB$	$BA+9+876-5+4321$
509A	08758	$-1+234+5-67^*-89+AB$	$B-A+987-(6-(-5+4321))$
509B	08759	$-12-34-56-7^*-89A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*765+43+2^*-1$
50A0	08760	$-1^*2^*-3^*(-45-6+78+9AB)$	$BA+9-8-7-65^*-4^*(3+21)$
50A1	08761	$-12+3+4567+89^*A+B$	$B-(A-9-8^*765+4)+3^*21$
50A2	08762	$-1+23-4^*(-5-67)^*(-89+AB)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^*(5+4)^3+2-1$
50A3	08763	$1-(-2-345-6-78^*9^*A+B)$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6)^*5^*4-3^*2+1$
50A4	08764	$-123+4-5^*-6+7^*89A+B$	$-B+A+9-8^*-765+43+21$
50A5	08765	$-12-(-345-67^*89-A)-B$	$B+A^*9-8^*(-765-(-4+3))-(-2+1)$
50A6	08766	$-1-(2-34^*-56)-(7-8^*9AB)$	$-B+A+987-6+5+4321$
50A7	08767	$-123+45+6-7^*-89A-B$	$BA+9+876+5+4321$
50A8	08768	$-12+3-4+5^*-6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$-B+A+987+6-5+4321$
50A9	08769	$-1-(-23-4567-8^*-9A+B)$	$B+A-(-9^*-8^*7-6^*-543^*2^*-1)$
50AA	08770	$-1-2-(34+56-7^*89A+B)$	$BA-(9-87^*-6-5432-1)$
50AB	08771	$1+23+45^*(6-7)-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B+A^*-9+8^*(765-4-(-3-21))$
50B0	08772	$-1^*(2+34-(-5+6-7^*(-89A+B)))$	$-B-A^*9^*(-87+6-(5-4))-32+1$
50B1	08773	$123-4+5678-9^*A^*B$	$-BA+987^*6+54+321$
50B2	08774	$12+345-(-6-78^*-9^*-A)-B$	$-BA98+76-54^*-321$
50B3	08775	$1-2-3-4+5^*-6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$B-(-A+9^*(-87-6)^*(5+4))+3^*-21$
50B4	08776	$-1+23+4567-89^*-A-B$	$B-A^*9+8^*765-(-4+3)^*-21$
50B5	08777	$-1-2^*(345-(67+8)-(-9-A))^*-B$	$-B-(A-987-6^*5)+4321$
50B6	08778	$1-2+345+67^*89+A-B$	$B+A+987-6-5+4321$
50B7	08779	$-1+2-(3-(-4+5+67))^*(-8-9+AB)$	$B-A9-87-6^*5^*4^*3^*-21$
50B8	08780	$1^*(-2-3)^*(-456-789+A-B)$	$B-A+987+6+5+4321$
50B9	08781	$-12-34-56-7^*-89A+B$	$BA+987^*6+5^*(43+2^*-1)$
50BA	08782	$-1-2-3+45+678^*9+AB$	$-BA9+876+5432-1$
50BB	08783	$12+34^*-56-7+8^*9AB$	$-BA9+876-5432^*-1$
5100	08784	$1-(-2-345+67^*-89+A)+B$	$-BA9+876-(-5432-1)$
5101	08785	$1^*-2+34-56+7^*(89A-B)$	$B+A9-8^*-765-(-4+32+1)$
5102	08786	$123+45+6^*(-7+8)^*9AB$	$BA+9+87^*-6+5432-1$
5103	08787	$-1234-5^*6-(78-9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9/8^*(7+6^*5+4+3+2)^1$
5104	08788	$1-(-2+3-45-678^*9-AB)$	$B+A9-8^*-765-4-3-21$
5105	08789	$-123+4-5-6-7^*(-89A-B)$	$-B^*(-A98-(7+6)-(-543+2)+1)$
5106	08790	$-1234-5+6+78^*9A-B$	$-B+A9-8+765^*4^*(3-2+1)$
5107	08791	$1-2-(-3-(4^5+6)+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9-8+7^*(-6+54)^*(-3+21)$
5108	08792	$-123-4+56+7^*89A+B$	$B-A-9+8^*(-76-5+43)^*-21$
5109	08793	$-123-(4+5-6+7^*(-89A-B))$	$-B+A9+8^*765+4-3^*(2+1)$
510A	08794	$12+345+67^*-89^*(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8^*765-(4-3+2)-1$
510B	08795	$1-2^*(3+456)^*-7-89-AB$	$-BA9+876-5432^*-1$
5110	08796	$1+234-(5+6^*(7-(-8+9AB)))$	$B+A9+8^*765+4-3-21$
5111	08797	$-12-3^*-45-6^*(7-8-9AB)$	$B+A9-8^*(-765+4-(3-2))+1$
5112	08798	$-12+3-4-56+7^*89A-B$	$BA+9-(8^*-765-4)-(-32-1)$
5113	08799	$12-3+45+678^*9+AB$	$B-A+987+6^*5+4321$
5114	08800	$1^*2^*-34^*(-56-7^*-8+9)^*A^*B$	$-B-A9^*-87-6^*(543-21)$
5115	08801	$12-(-3-4)-((-5-678)^*9-AB)$	$BA9-8^*(-76-543-21)$
5116	08802	$1-23+4-(-5-6)+7^*(89A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6+5^*4^3/2-1$
5117	08803	$-123-4+5+6+7^*(89A+B)$	$-B+A^*-9^*(-87+6-5+4)-3^*2^*1$
5118	08804	$1+23-4+(5+678)^*9+AB$	$B+A-9-8^*-765-4^*(-3-21)$
5119	08805	$12+3-(-45-678^*9-AB)$	$B+A9-8^*-765-(4^*3+2+1)$
511A	08806	$-12^*(3+4+567-8-9AB)$	$BA-9-(8^*(-765-4)+32)-1$
511B	08807	$1+234+5-678^*-9-AB$	$BA+9-8^*-765+4-3-21$
5120	08808	$123-4^*56-7^*-89A+B$	$BA9-8^*-76+5^*43^*21$
5121	08809	$-1-234^*-56-(-7+89)^*AB$	$B+A+9-8^*7+(6^*5+4^3)^2-1$
5122	08810	$1+2-(-3-4^*5^*-67+8^*9A^*B)$	$-B-A-987^*-6-5^*4+321$
5123	08811	$-123-(-4-5-6+7^*(-89A-B))$	$B-A-9-8^*-765^*(4-3)^*2^*-1$
5124	08812	$-1234-5+6+78^*9A+B$	$B+A-9-8+7+6^*5+4^3(3+2)+1$
5125	08813	$1-2-3+4-56-7^*-89A-B$	$B-A^*-9+8^*(765+4)-(-3-(-2-1))$
5126	08814	$123-4-5+6^*(7+8+9AB)$	$-B-A-98^*76+543^*21$
5127	08815	$-12-3-(45-6-7^*89A)-B$	$B-A9-(-8+7^*(-6+5)^*43^*21)$
5128	08816	$-1-2+3^*-4^*(5+6-7^*89)+AB$	$B+A^*9+8^*765-4+32+1$
5129	08817	$-123+456^*-7^*(8-9+A-B)$	$B+A+98-765^*-4^*(3-2+1)$
512A	08818	$-1+2-3-45-6+7^*89A-B$	$B-(-A9+8^*-765)-(-4+3)-(-2+1)$
512B	08819	$1-2+3^*(-4+5)^*(6+78)^*(9A+B)$	$-B-(-A98+76)-(-5-4321)$
5130	08820	$-12^*(-3-456-78+9A-B)$	$BA-9-8^*(-765+4)-(-32-1)$
5131	08821	$-123+4567-(-89A-B)$	$-B+A-9-8^*-765+4^*32-1$
5132	08822	$-1234+5-(-6+78^*-9A-B)$	$-B+A9-8^*-765+4^*(3+2+1)$
5133	08823	$12-34-5^*6+7^*89A-B$	$B-(-A+9-8^*765+43^*(-2-1))$
5134	08824	$-12-(34-5)-(6-7^*89A+B)$	$-B-A-(-987-65)+4321$
5135	08825	$-12-(3+45+6)-(-7^*89A-B)$	$-B-A+(98-7)^*65-4+321$
5136	08826	$12+3-4-56-7^*-89A-B$	$B+A-9+8+7+6^*5+4^3(3+2)-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5137	08827	$1*(-23-4-56)*(-7-(89-A-B))$	$BA-9-8^*-765+4^*3+2^*1$
5138	08828	$-1^*2*(-3456-7-8+9AB)$	$-B-A^*-9^*-8^*(-7-6)-(54+321)$
5139	08829	$123-(-45-678^*9+A-B)$	$-B+A98-76+5+4321$
513A	08830	$-123+4567-8+9A^*B$	$-B+A98-(7-(-65+4321))$
513B	08831	$-12+34^*-5^*6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A9-(-8^*765+4)-(-32+1)$
5140	08832	$123-(45-678^*9+A^*B)$	$-BA-98-76^*(-54-32+1)$
5141	08833	$1-(2-3+4)-(56+7^*-89A)+B$	$B+A9-(-8^*765+4^*3-21)$
5142	08834	$-12^*(3-(456-7)-(8-9))^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A98^*-76+543^*21$
5143	08835	$1-2-3+4-56+7^*89A+B$	$-B+A^*9^*(-8-7)^*-6+543-21$
5144	08836	$-1-2-(34-56)+7^*(89A-B)$	$B-A-98^*76+543^*21$
5145	08837	$-12-3-(45-6-7^*89A-B)$	$-B+A9+8-(-7^*6^*-5^*(-4-32))-1$
5146	08838	$-1234+5678+9A^*B$	$B-A^*98^*(-7-6+5)-(-4+321)$
5147	08839	$-12+34-56-7^*-89A-B$	$BA+9+8+765^*(4+3+2-1)$
5148	08840	$-1+2-(34-(56-7^*(-89A+B)))$	$-B+A9+8^*765+4^*-32^*-1$
5149	08841	$1-2^(3+4)^*((-5-6)^*7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A98-(76+5-4321)$
514A	08842	$123+4-(-5-(67-8))^*(-9+AB)$	$B+A^*-9^*(-87-65)-4321$
514B	08843	$-12+3-45+6+7^*89A+B$	$B+A+9^*8-7^*6^*5^*4^*-3^*(2-1)$
5150	08844	$-123+4+5-6+7^*(8+9-AB)$	$-B^*(-A9+8+7-65-432+1)$
5151	08845	$-1234-(-56+78^*-9A+B)$	$BA-(9+8^*-765-4-3-21)$
5152	08846	$-123+4567-(-8-9A^*B)$	$B-(A-987-65-4321)$
5153	08847	$-1-2-34-5-6-7^*-89A+B$	$B+A+9^*8+7+6^*(5+4)^*3^*2-1$
5154	08848	$-12^*(-345-6+7-(8+9+AB))$	$-BA-9-(8-7)-6^*-5^*4^*3^*21$
5155	08849	$1-23-4+56-7^*(-89A+B)$	$-B+A^*98^*7-6+543-21$
5156	08850	$1-2-3-(45-6-7^*89A)+B$	$-B+A9+8^*765+43+2-1$
5157	08851	$1+(2^*3^*4^*5)^*(6+7^*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A98-76+5+4321$
5158	08852	$1^*-2^*(-3-45^*67-89-AB)$	$B+A98-7-65+4321$
5159	08853	$1-2^*345^*6+(7+89)^*AB$	$BA98-7-65^*4^*32^*1$
515A	08854	$-12-345-67+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A9-8^*-765-4+32^*1$
515B	08855	$-123+45+6+7^*(89A+B)$	$BA+9-8^*-765-4+3+21$
5160	08856	$-1^*234^*(-5^*(-6+7)-(-8+9+A+B))$	$B+A-98^*76+543^*21$
5161	08857	$1^*-2+345+67^*(89-A+B)$	$BA+9-8^*-765+43-21$
5162	08858	$-12-34+5+6+7^*89A+B$	$B+A+(9+8^*7+6+5^*4+3)^*2+1$
5163	08859	$1+23-4-56-7^*-89A+B$	$-B-A+9^*(876-5^*43)-2-1$
5164	08860	$1-23-4+5+6-7^*-89A-B$	$-BA-987^*-6-5+432-1$
5165	08861	$1-2-(34+5-6)-(7^*-89A-B)$	$BA-9-8^*-765+43-(2+1)$
5166	08862	$12^*(-345-(-67+89^*-A+B))$	$BA-9+8^*765+43-2^*1$
5167	08863	$12-3^*(4-5^*(6+7-8)^*9A)+B$	$BA-(-9+8^*(-765-4))-(-3+2+1)$
5168	08864	$12-34-5-6+7^*89A+B$	$BA98-76^*5^*(43-21)$
5169	08865	$-1+23-(-4+56)-7^*-89A+B$	$BA+9-(8^*-765-(-4+32)^*1)$
516A	08866	$-1-(2+3-45-6)+7^*(89A-B)$	$BA98-(-7+65^*4^*32)-1$
516B	08867	$-1234-(-56-78^*9A-B)$	$-B+A98+7^*-6-5+4321$
5170	08868	$1-2-3-4^*(-567+8-9AB)$	$-B+A9+8^*(765+4)-32^*-1$
5171	08869	$-12+34+5^*6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^*5+4^*(3+2)+1$
5172	08870	$1-23-(4-5)-6+7^*89A+B$	$-B+A9-8^*(765+4+3+2)^*-1$
5173	08871	$-12+3+4567-8+9^*AB$	$B+A9-8^*-765+43^*(2-1)$
5174	08872	$-1^*2^*(-3456+78-9A^*-B)$	$BA+9-8^*-765-(-4-32)-1$
5175	08873	$-1234+56-(78-9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8^*7+(6+5^*4)^*3/2-1$
5176	08874	$1+2+3^*-45+6^*-7^*(-89-A^*B)$	$B-A9^*(8-7-(6+54))-32^*1$
5177	08875	$1+2-34-(-5-6)+7^*89A+B$	$-B-A9+8+7+6^*5^*4^*-3^*21$
5178	08876	$-1+2-(-3-4^*(567-8+9AB))$	$B-A-9-8/-7^*(6^*5-4^*(3+2^*1))$
5179	08877	$-1-(23-4)-(56+7^*(-89A-B))$	$B^*(A-98+7-(-654-3+21))$
517A	08878	$-1-(2+3-4-(-5+6))-7^*(89A-B)$	$BA9-8^*7^*(-65-43)-2-1$
517B	08879	$-1-(2-(-3+4^*5-6^*7+8)^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9^*-8^*(-7+6^*-5-4)^*3+2^*1$
5180	08880	$123+4567+8+9^*-A^*-B$	$BA9+8-7^*-6^*-5+4321$
5181	08881	$-1^*(-2+3-(4567-8)-9^*AB)$	$B+A-987^*-6+5+4+321$
5182	08882	$1234+5^*(-6-7)^*-89-(A-B)$	$-B-A+987^*6+5^*-43^*-2-1$
5183	08883	$12-3+4^*(567-8+9AB)$	$-BA-98+7-6+5^*-4^*-321$
5184	08884	$123+4-(5+678^*-9)-A^*-B$	$B+A-9-8/-7^*(6^*5-4-3^*(2+1))$
5185	08885	$-123-(4-5^*6-7^*(-8+9A^*B))$	$B-A-98+76^*5^*4^*(3+2)^*1$
5186	08886	$1+2+3^*4+5^*-6-7^*-89A+B$	$BA+9^*-8^*7-(6-5432)^*1$
5187	08887	$-12+3-(-4567-8)+9^*AB$	$BA+9+8^*7^*6^*(54-32)^*1$
5188	08888	$1+2+3+4567-8+9^*AB$	$BA+9^*876-54^*32^*1$
5189	08889	$12+3-4^*(-567+8-9AB)$	$BA-(9-8^*765)-(-43-21)$
518A	08890	$-123-45-6^*(-78-9AB)$	$BA-9^*8^*7+6^*543^*2^*1$
518B	08891	$1+2^*-34+56^*-7+8^*9^*AB$	$-B+A9^*(-8-(-7-6)+54)-(-3-2^*-1)$
5190	08892	$-123^*-4^*(-56+7+8^*-9^*(A-B))$	$BA-9+8^*765+4-3^*-21$
5191	08893	$-1234-(5-6)-78^*(-9-A^*B)$	$B+A+9-8/-7^*(6^*5-4^*(3+2))-1$
5192	08894	$1-(2+3-(4567+8))+9^*AB$	$-BA-9+(8+7)^*6(-5+432)^*-1$
5193	08895	$12-34+(-56-7^*89-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9^*(8-7^*6-5+4^*(3+2)+1)$
5194	08896	$-1+2-3+4567+8-9^*-AB$	$-B-(-A98+7-(-6-(5-4321)))$
5195	08897	$-12+34+56+7^*89+AB$	$-B-(-A+98^*-76+543^*2^*1)$
5196	08898	$1+2-(3-(4567+8)-9^*AB)$	$-BA-(-9+87+6-5^*4^*321)$
5197	08899	$12+3-(-4-5+6-7^*89A+B)$	$B^*(-A-98-(-76+543+2))^*-1$
5198	08900	$-1-2^*3^*-45+678^*9-A-B$	$BA+9-(-8^*(765+4)-(-32-1))$
5199	08901	$1-2^*-3^*-45-(678-9A)^*-B$	$B+A+9^*8+7+6^*5+4^*(3+2)+1$
519A	08902	$-1-(-2-3)-(-4567-8)-9^*-AB$	$BA9-87-65+4321$
519B	08903	$-12-34^*56+7-89^*-A^*B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+(6^*5+4^*3)^*2-1$
51A0	08904	$1-2-3-4+5+6-7^*-89A+B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+(6^*5+4^*3)^*2^*1$
51A1	08905	$-12+34+56-7^*(-89A+B)$	$-BA-98-(76-5432+1)$
51A2	08906	$-123+45-6-7^*(8-9A^*B)$	$-B+A98-(7+6-5-4321)$
51A3	08907	$1-2+3-(-4+56-7^*(89A+B))$	$-BA-98-76-(-5432-1)$
51A4	08908	$-1-2-(-34+5^*6+7^*-89A)+B$	$-B+A98-7+6-5+4321$
51A5	08909	$1+234+5^*-6^*(-78+9A)^*-B$	$-BA+9-8-76+5^*-4^*-321$
51A6	08910	$1+23-(-4567+8)-9^*-AB$	$BA+9+8^*765+4-3^*-21$
51A7	08911	$12+3+4-5-6-7^*-89A+B$	$BA+987+6-5+4321$
51A8	08912	$-123+4+5-6+7^*(-89-A)-B$	$B-(-A+98-7)+6^*-5^*-4^*-3^*-21$
51A9	08913	$-1-2-34-(5+6)+7^*(89A+B)$	$-B+A-98-7^*6^*-5^*(4-(-32-1))$
51AA	08914	$1+2+34+56+7^*89+AB$	$B+A+9+8+7^*(6+5^*4+3)^*2^*1$
51AB	08915	$12+3-4-5+6+7^*89A+B$	$B+A+9+8-7^*(-6-(5^*4+3))^*2+1$
51B0	08916	$1+(-2/-3+4^*5-6^*7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B-(A-987^*6)+54+321$
51B1	08917	$1-(2-34)-(-5+6)-(-7^*89A+B)$	$B+A+9-8/-7^*(6^*5-(4-3-2))-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
51B2	08918	$12^*(-3+4-567+8+9AB)$	$B+A98-7-(6+5)+4321$
51B3	08919	$12-(34-56-7^*89A)-B$	$-B-(A-98^*76)+5^*-4^*-3^*-21$
51B4	08920	$-1-(-2-34-56+7^*(-89A+B))$	$-B-(-A98-7+6)-(-5-4321)$
51B5	08921	$123+4567+89^*A-B$	$BA+987+6+5+4321$
51B6	08922	$1^*2^*3^*(45+6-7-(-8-9AB))$	$-B+A98+7+6-5+4321$
51B7	08923	$1+2+34-(5-6+7^*-89A+B)$	$B+A+9+8^*7+(6^*5+4^*3)^2+1$
51B8	08924	$-1-(-23-4567)-(-8-9^*AB)$	$B-A9-8-76+5^*-4^*-321$
51B9	08925	$123-45-6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$B-A9-87+6+5^*-4^*-321$
51BA	08926	$1+2+3-(45-6)-7^*(-89A-B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7+6^*(5+4)^3)^2-1$
51BB	08927	$12-3^*-4-56-7^*(-89A-B)$	$B-(A-9-8^*-7^*6-(5432-1))$
5200	08928	$12+34^*-5+6^*(78+9AB)$	$B+A98-7-6-(-5-4321)$
5201	08929	$1-2+34-(5+6+7^*-89A)+B$	$B+A+98^*7^*(6+5)+4-(3+21)$
5202	08930	$-1-2+3^*-4-(-56-7^*89A)-B$	$B+A98-7-(-6+5-4321)$
5203	08931	$1+2345-6^*78^*-9+A+B$	$-B-A9+8^*(765+43-2)-1$
5204	08932	$-12-3+4+56-7^*-89A-B$	$B^*(A-9^*(-8-76+5))+4-(32+1)$
5205	08933	$1+23-(4-5^*6+7^*-89A+B)$	$B-A^*-98^*7+6+543+21$
5206	08934	$1^*-2^*3^*(-45-(-6+7)-(-8+9AB))$	$B+A+9-(-8-7-6^*5)^4/(3+2^*-1)$
5207	08935	$1+234-(-5678-9^*A^*-B)$	$B+A+9^*8+7+(6^*5+4^*3)^2-1$
5208	08936	$1-2-34+(5+6)^*78^*-9-AB$	$B+A+9^*8+7+(6^*5+4^*3)^2*1$
5209	08937	$12-3-(-45+6+7^*-89A)-B$	$-B-A^*9+8-7^*6^*-5^*(4+32+1)$
520A	08938	$123+45+678^*9+A^*B$	$B+A-9+8-7^*(6-5^*4^*(3+2-1))$
520B	08939	$1+2-(-3-(4^*5-6^*7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+(8^*-7+6)^*-5^*4)^*3^2-1$
5210	08940	$-12+345^*-6^*-7+8^*-9AB$	$B+A98-7+6+5+4321$
5211	08941	$-12-(-3+4+5)-6-7^*(-89A-B)$	$B+A^*(-98+765-(43+21))$
5212	08942	$-1-23+4567+89A-B$	$B-(-A98-(7-6+5)-4321)$
5213	08943	$-1^*(23-(4567+89A)+B)$	$-B^*(-A98-765+4^*321)$
5214	08944	$1-23+4567+89A-B$	$B+A98+7+6-5+4321$
5215	08945	$1-2-345^*(6+7)+89AB$	$B-A9-8^*(-765-43)-21$
5216	08946	$1-2345+6+78^*(9+AB)$	$BA^*(-9-8+7-6^*5+4+321)$
5217	08947	$-1+2-345+6-7-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*7^*-6^*-5^*(4-3/2)+1$
5218	08948	$1-23+4+56^*-7-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7-6^*5)^4*3/2-1$
5219	08949	$-1+2-345-6-(-7+8^*9^*-AB)$	$BA9-8^*7-(65-4321)$
521A	08950	$1+2^*-34+(567+89)^*A-B$	$-BA+9^*-8-76-5432^*-1$
521B	08951	$1-(2-3-4-56-7^*89A+B)$	$-BA-9^*8-76+5432+1$
5220	08952	$-1+2+3+45-6+7^*89A+B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(7-(-6^*-5^*-4+3))^2+1$
5221	08953	$-12-3+4567-(-89A+B)$	$-BA-9+8^*(-765-43-2)^*-1$
5222	08954	$12-(-34-5+6)-(-7^*89A-B)$	$B+A98-(-7-(6-(-5-4321)))$
5223	08955	$12+34-56-7^*(-89A-B)$	$BA+9-8^*7^*6^*-5^*-4^*321$
5224	08956	$12+34-5-(-6+7^*-89A)+B$	$B+A+9+8-7^*(6-5^*4^*(3+2-1))$
5225	08957	$1-2+345-678^*-9-AB$	$-B-A^*9-(-8+76-5^*4^*321)$
5226	08958	$12+3-(4-56)-(-7^*89A+B)$	$B-A-(-98^*(-7+65+4+3)-21)$
5227	08959	$-123+4567-(8-9AB)$	$B+A98-7+6^*5+4321$
5228	08960	$-12^*34^*(5-6+78-9A+B)$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7+6)+(5^*4)^3+2+1$
5229	08961	$-1+23-(-4+56^*(7+8))^*9-A)+B$	$-B+A98-7^*-6+5+4321$
522A	08962	$-1+23+4^*(567+8+9AB)$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)+4/3)^*(2+1)$
522B	08963	$12-(3+4+5+6)+7^*(89A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7^*-6^*-5^*(4-3/2)-1)$
5230	08964	$-1-(23-4567)-(-89A-B)$	$-B-A-98^*7^*-6+(5+4)^*321$
5231	08965	$1^*-23+4567+89A+B$	$B^*(A-98-76-(5+432))^*-1$
5232	08966	$1-2-3+4567+89A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6^*5^*(4^*3^2+1))$
5233	08967	$-1234+5678+9AB$	$B+A-9^*(-87-654+32-1)$
5234	08968	$12+345^*6^*7-8^*9AB$	$-B-A+9^*(87+65)+4321$
5235	08969	$-1^*(-2+3-4567-89A+B)$	$B+A+9^*8+7^*(6+5^*4+3)^2*1$
5236	08970	$1+2-(-3^*-4^*-5-6+7^*-89A)+B$	$B-A-98^*7^*(-6-5)-(-4^*-3-21)$
5237	08971	$1-(23+4+5+6+7^*(8+9-AB))$	$B+A-9-8/-7^*(6^*5+4^*3)-(2-1)$
5238	08972	$-1^*(2-3-4-56+7^*-89A-B)$	$-BA-98+76+5^*4^*321$
5239	08973	$-1-23+4567-8-9A^*-B$	$B+A98+7^*6-(5-4321)$
523A	08974	$-1-(-2+3)-(-4567+(-89-A)^*B)$	$B+A-9-8/-7^*(6^*5+4^*3)+2^*1$
523B	08975	$-123+4567+8+9AB$	$B+A-9-8/-7^*(6^*5+4^*3)+2+1$
5240	08976	$-1-2^*-3+4^*(-5+6)+7^*(89A+B)$	$B^*(A9-87-6+543+21)$
5241	08977	$1-2^*-3-(-4567-89A)-B$	$BA-98^*76-543^*-21$
5242	08978	$-123-45+(-6+78)^*(9A-B)$	$-BA-9^*(8+7)^*-65-43^*21$
5243	08979	$-1+2^*345-6^*(78-9AB)$	$BA9-8-(76+5)+4321$
5244	08980	$123-4-(56-7^*89A)-B$	$BA9-(87-6)-5+4321$
5245	08981	$-12+3+4567+89A+B$	$-B-A-987^*-6-5+432-1$
5246	08982	$-1^*2^*3^*(-4+5-(67-(8-9AB)))$	$-BA-98-7-6+5432-1$
5247	08983	$-12-34-5^*67-8^*-9^*AB$	$-BA-(98+7+6+5432^*-1)$
5248	08984	$-12-3+4567-(8+9A^*-B)$	$-B+A98-7+65+4321$
5249	08985	$1^*(2-3-4)^*(-567-(8+9^*A^*B))$	$B+A+9^*(8-7^*6+5+4^*(3+2)+1)$
524A	08986	$-1-2-3+4567+89A+B$	$-BA+9-(8+7+6)-5^*4^*-321$
524B	08987	$12+3+4567-(-89A+B)$	$BA+987-(-65-4321)$
5250	08988	$123+4-56+7^*89A-B$	$-BA-98-7+6^*543^*2+1$
5251	08989	$-1+23-4+56+7^*89A+B$	$-B-A+9+8-7-6^*-5^*4^*3^*21$
5252	08990	$-1+2-3+4567-(-89A-B)$	$BA9-(87-6)-(-5-4321)$
5253	08991	$123-4^*-5+(67-8+9)^*-A^*-B$	$-B+A9+8^*(765+4^*3^*2)+1$
5254	08992	$1+2-3-(-4567-89A-B)$	$BA+987^*6-5+4+321$
5255	08993	$-12+34+56-(-7^*89A-B)$	$BA-987^*-6+(-5+4)^*-321$
5256	08994	$-1+234^*5^*6-7^*89A+A^*-B$	$-BA-9-87-6-5432^*-1$
5257	08995	$-12+3-(4-5)^*67^*(-8-(9-AB))$	$BA9+8-76-5+4321$
5258	08996	$-1-(-2-3-4567-(89A+B))$	$-BA-(98-7+6-5432+1)$
5259	08997	$-12-(3-45+6+7^*(-89A-B))$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(76-5-432+1)$
525A	08998	$-1+2-3+4+5^*-6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$-B+A98+7+65+4321$
525B	08999	$12-3+456^*7^*(8+9-(A-B))$	$-B+A98+76-(5-4321)$
5260	09000	$-12-(3-4567)-(-8-9A^*B)$	$-BA-98+7+6^*543^*2-1$
5261	09001	$-1-2+3+4567-(8-9A^*B)$	$-B+A^*9^*87-6-5^*4^*3-(-2-1)$
5262	09002	$-12-3-(-45-6)^*7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A9^*-87-6543^*2^*1$
5263	09003	$12-345-6^*-7+8^*9^*AB$	$B-A-987^*-6-(5-432+1)$
5264	09004	$-1-2-(-34-56)-(-7^*-89A-B)$	$-B-A9-87-6+5432-1$
5265	09005	$12+34-(-5-67)^*89+AB$	$-BA-9-8-76-5432^*-1$
5266	09006	$1-2-(-34-56)+7^*89A+B$	$B+A98-7+65+4321$
5267	09007	$1-(2-34+5-6)-7^*(-89A-B)$	$-BA-9-87+6+5432+1$
5268	09008	$1+2^*3+4^*5^*(6^*7+8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA-98+7+6+5432-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5269	09009	-1234-56+789*A+B	-B+A98+76+5+4321
526A	09010	-1+234*5*6-78*9+A-B	-BA-98+7+6-(-5432-1)
526B	09011	1-(23-4)-(-56-7*(89A+B))	-BA-(-9+87)-(6-5432+1)
5270	09012	12-3+4567-8+9A*B	-BA+9-87-6+5432*1
5271	09013	1-234*5*6-78*9*(A+B)	B-(A9+8+7-6-5*4*321)
5272	09014	-1*-2^3*(4^5-(-6-7)*8)-9+A-B	-B+A-9-8*(-765-4-32-1)
5273	09015	-1+2-3-(-4567-8+9A*B)	B-A-(-987*6-5-432)+1
5274	09016	1+2-3-4+(-5+6-78+9)*A*B	-B-(A9+87-6-5432)-1
5275	09017	-1-(2-3)+4567-(-8+9A*B)	-B-A9-(87-6)+5432*1
5276	09018	-1+23-(-4567-89A)+B	-B-A9-87+6-(-5432-1)
5277	09019	1-2+3-(-4567-8-9A*B)	B+A+9*(8+7*6)*5*4-3+2-1
5278	09020	1+23-(-4567-89A)+B	B*A*(9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2-1)
5279	09021	12+34+56+7*89A+B	B-(-A98-76-(-5+4321))
527A	09022	-123-4-5-(6-78)*(9A-B)	-BA-9-(-8+76-5432)+1
527B	09023	1-2+3-45-67*(-89-A)-B	-BA+9-87-(-6-5432)-1
5280	09024	1*-2*3*(4-56-7-8-9AB)	-BA+9-87+6+5432*1
5281	09025	-123-4*(5-6+78+9A)*B	-BA+9-87-(-6-5432)+1
5282	09026	1+2-3*4+5-67*(8-(-9+AB))	-B-A-98-76+5432-1
5283	09027	-1+2-345-(-67+8*9*A-B)	BA9-8*7+6-5+4321
5284	09028	12-3+4567-(-8-9A*B)	B-A9-87-6+5432+1
5285	09029	1-(-23-4567+8)+9A*B	BA9-87*-65-(432+1)
5286	09030	-1+2*(3-4)+56+7*(89A+B)	-B-A*9*(-87-6)-543+2*1
5287	09031	123+45-6-7*(-89A+B)	B+A98+76+5+4321
5288	09032	-12+3-45+67*(89A)+B	-B-A9-(-8+76)-5432*-1
5289	09033	-1-23-45-6*(-78-9AB)	-B-A9+8-(76-5432-1)
528A	09034	-1+2*3*-45-67-8*9*-AB	B+A-9*8-(-7*(6^(5-(4-3))+2)+1)
528B	09035	1+2^3-(-4^5+6+7+8)*9+A-B	-BA+9-87*(65+4*-3)-(-2+1)
5290	09036	1234+5*(6-(-78-9A*B))	B-A-9+(8-7+6*5+4^3)^2-1
5291	09037	-12-34-5+67*(89A)+B	BA9-8+7*-6+5+4321
5292	09038	-1-(-2-34-5*6+7*(-89A-B))	-BA-(-9-8+76-5432+1)
5293	09039	(1^2-3)^4*5*((-6-7)*8-9)+A-B	-BA+9+8-(76-5432*1)
5294	09040	-1-23+4-56-(78-9)*A*B	-BA+9+8-76+5432+1
5295	09041	-1-2*3-(-4^5+6+7+8)*9+A+B	B-A-9+8*7*6*5+4321
5296	09042	-1*2-3*(-4+5-6*7*8)*9+A-B	-B*(A9-8-(-7+654)+3-21)
5297	09043	123+4-5-6-7*-89A-B	-B+A*-98*7-(-654-(3+2))+1
5298	09044	12-3-4+5*6-7+8*9*-AB	-B-(-A9-8-7*-6+5-43*-21))
5299	09045	1+23+4567+8+9A*B	-BA+9*8+7+6*-543*2*-1
529A	09046	1+2-3*45+(-6+78)*(9A-B)	-B+A-98-76+5432-1
529B	09047	1-(-2-3)-(-4-5*-67+8*-9*A-B)	-B+A-98-76+5432*1
52A0	09048	-123-45*-6+7*89A+B	-B-A-9+8*-7-(-6-5*-4*-321)
52A1	09049	1+2-3*(-4+5-6*7*8)*9-(A-B)	B-A-(98+76-5432*1)
52A2	09050	-1-(2-34+5*6*(-7-8-9AB))	B-A-98-76+5432+1
52A3	09051	-1-2+3*-4*5+6*(78+9AB)	BA9-(8-7-6*-5-4321)
52A4	09052	-123+4567+8*9*(A+B)	-BA-9-8-7*6-(-5432+1)
52A5	09053	1234+5+6-7*(-8-9*-A*-B)	-B*(-A+9-8*-76-543*-2*-1)
52A6	09054	-12+345-678*-9-A-B	B+A9+8-(76+5432*-1)
52A7	09055	-12-(34+5+6*(-78-9AB))	BA9-8+7*6*5*(-4+32+1)
52A8	09056	1*(-2-345-67)*(-8-9-A+B)	BA9-(87-65)+4321
52A9	09057	123-4+5+6+7*89A-B	B+A987*6-(-54-321)
52AA	09058	-1*(-234+5-678*9-AB)	B+A9+8*-7*6-5432*-1
52AB	09059	-12-(-34-56+7*(-89A-B))	B-A+9+8*-7*-6*5+4321
52B0	09060	1+2-(3+456)+7*(-8-9A)*B	BA9+8*(-7+654-3)+2+1
52B1	09061	-1-2+3-45-6*(-78-9AB)	BA9-8*-7-65+4321
52B2	09062	12-(3+4+5*(67*-8-9*AB))	B+A+9+8+(-7*(6-5*4)-3)^2-1
52B3	09063	-123*(4-5)*(-67-8+9+AB)	-B-(A9+8-7*-6-5432+1)
52B4	09064	-1234-5+6+789*A-B	-BA+98-76*(-54-32+1)
52B5	09065	-123-4-56*-7*(8-9+A+B)	B-A9-(-87-65)*43-(-2-1)
52B6	09066	1-(-2+3*-4)-((-567-89)*A-B)	BA9-8-(7+6-5)+4321
52B7	09067	1-2+345-678*-9-A-B	BA9+8+7-6*5+4321
52B8	09068	123-4-56-7*(-89A-B)	B-(-A-(-98-76))-(-5432+1)
52B9	09069	1-23*45+6*78*(-9-A)+B	B+A-98-76-5432*-1
52BA	09070	-1+2-(-34+5)-6*(-78-9AB)	BA9-8+7-6-5+4321
52BB	09071	12-3-4-56+(78-9)*A*B	-BA+9-8*7+6+5432*1
5300	09072	12*(3+456-(78-9A)+B)	BA9+8-7-6-(5-4321)
5301	09073	-1-(-2+34-5*-6-7*(8-9A*-B))	B+A+9-87+6-5*4*-321
5302	09074	-1234+5+6-789*-A-B	BA-98*(-7-6-54)-3-(-2-1)
5303	09075	-1*(2+3)*(4-56+7+8-9A)*B	B-A9-8*7-6+5432+1
5304	09076	1+234-56-7*(-89A+B)	BA-98-76-5*4*-321
5305	09077	12+3-456-7*(-8-9A)*B	-B+A*-9*-87+6*-5-4*32*1
5306	09078	1+2-345+678*(9-A)+B	BA9-8-7+6-(-5-4321)
5307	09079	123-(45+6-7*(89A+B))	-BA9-8+76*-5*-4*3*-2*-1
5308	09080	1-234+5678-9*(A+B)	BA9-8*(-7+654)*(-3+2)-1
5309	09081	-1-23-(-45+678+9)*A-B	-BA-9-8-7-6-(-5432+1)
530A	09082	123+456+78*-9*-A-B	BA9+8-7-(6-5-4321)
530B	09083	-1-2-(-3+45)-6+7*(8+9A*B)	-BA-9-8-7-6+5432+1
5310	09084	1+23*(4-5)*-6*-7*8*(9-A)+B	BA9-(-8+7)-(-6+5-4321)
5311	09085	-1-2-3*4+5*-6-(-78+9)*A*B	-BA-98-76+5432-1
5312	09086	12*(-34+5-(-6+7-89)-A)*B	-B-A-(-9-8)+76*(54+32-1)
5313	09087	1-23*-4-(-5-6+7*(-89A-B))	-BA-(98-76)-(-5432-1)
5314	09088	12-345+67*(-8+9A+B)	-BA+9+8+7*-6+5432+1
5315	09089	1-23-4+5+6*(78+9AB)	B+A-9+8+7*6^(5-4+3)-2-1
5316	09090	-123+456*-7+89*AB	B+A+9*8*7*6^(5-4)*3-2-1
5317	09091	-1+2+345-678*-9-A+B	-BA-9*(-87-654+3+2)-1
5318	09092	-1234-56+78*(-9+AB)	BA9-8+7+6+5+4321
5319	09093	12-34-5-6-(-78+9)*A*-B	-BA-9-8-7-(-6-5432)-1
531A	09094	-1*-2*(-3+4+5-6*-7*8+9AB)	BA9+8-7+6+5+4321
531B	09095	((1+2+3)^4-(5-6))*7+8+9A+B	B-A-9+8+7-6*-5*4*3*21
5320	09096	12+34-56*(-7-(-8-9A+B))	BA9-(-8-7+6)+5+4321
5321	09097	-1-2+3+4567+(-8-9A)*B	-BA-9-8+7-(6-5432)+1
5322	09098	-1+23*-45*6+(7+8)*-9*-AB	-B-(A9+8+7+6*543*-2-1)
5323	09099	1-234-5+6-7+8*-9*-AB	-BA+9-8-7-6+5432-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5324	09100	$1+2-(-3-4*5+67*(-89-A)+B)$	$BA-98*7*(6+5)+43-21$
5325	09101	$1-234-5-6+7-8*9*-AB$	$B+A9+87*(6-(-5-43-21))$
5326	09102	$-1-23-(-4567+8-9AB)$	$BA-98*(-7-6-54)+3+21$
5327	09103	$12+345-678*9*(A-B)$	$-BA-(9-(8-7))-6*5432*2+1$
5328	09104	$1-23+4567-(8-9AB)$	$-BA+9-8-(7+6*-543*2*1)$
5329	09105	$1+23-4*-56-7*(-89A+B)$	$-B-A-98-7-6+5432+1$
532A	09106	$-1-23-4*-5+6*(78+9AB)$	$B-A-(-9-8*(765-(-43-2+1)))$
532B	09107	$123+4*(567+8+9AB)$	$-BA-9-8+7+6+5432-1$
5330	09108	$-1-2-3-(-4+5)*6*(-78-9AB)$	$BA9+87-65+4321$
5331	09109	$1-2*(34+5-(6-7))**(8-9A+B)$	$-BA-9-8+7-(-6-5432-1)$
5332	09110	$1-2-(-3*(4-5))-6*(78+9AB))$	$-B-A9+8-7-6+5432+1$
5333	09111	$1+2+3*4-(-56-7*(-8+9A*B))$	$-BA-9+8-7+6+5432+1$
5334	09112	$123+4-5*6-7*(-89A-B)$	$-BA-9-(-8-7+6-5432*1)$
5335	09113	$-12-3-(-4567+8)+9AB$	$BA9+8+(-7-65)*4*(3-21)$
5336	09114	$-123+45*6-7*(-89A-B)$	$-B-A-9-87-6+5432-1$
5337	09115	$-1-(23-4*56-7*89A+B)$	$-B-A-98-7+6+5432-1$
5338	09116	$-1-(-234+56-7*(-89-A))*-B)$	$B-A9-8-(7+6)+5432+1$
5339	09117	$1-2+3-4+5-6*(-78-9AB)$	$-B-A-(98+7-(6+5432+1))$
533A	09118	$-1-23+4567+8+9AB$	$BA-9*8*76*54*(-32-1)$
533B	09119	$-12+3-(-4567-(-8+9AB))$	$-B-(-A9-8+7-6*5*-4*-3*21)$
5340	09120	$123+4+56-7*-89A-B$	$BA9-8*(7-654)-(-32-1)$
5341	09121	$1+2*-3*(4-5)+6*(78+9AB)$	$-B-A9+8-(7-6)-5432*-1$
5342	09122	$123+456+7*(8+9*AB)$	$-B-A9+8-(-7+6)+5432-1$
5343	09123	$1+2*34-56*(7-8)+9-AB$	$-BA-(9-8-(7+6))-5432-1))$
5344	09124	$-1-2-(3-(4567-8)-9AB)$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5432*1$
5345	09125	$1-2+3-(-4-(5+6*(78+9AB)))$	$-BA-9+8+7+6+5432+1$
5346	09126	$1-(2+3-4567+8-9AB)$	$-B-A-9-87-(-6-5432+1)$
5347	09127	$-1-234+5678-(9+AB)$	$-B-A-9-8-76+5432+1$
5348	09128	$1234-56*(7-8)*(9A-B)$	$-BA+9*(87+654-3+2*1)$
5349	09129	$-12-3-(-4567-8-9AB)$	$-BA+9+8-(-7+6-5432+1)$
534A	09130	$1+2-3-(-4567+8-9AB)$	$B-A+98*(7+65)-(432+1)$
534B	09131	$-1+2+3+45-67*(-89-A)-B$	$-B-A-98+7-(-6-5432-1)$
5350	09132	$1-2+3+4567-8+9AB$	$-B-A+9-87-6+5432-1$
5351	09133	$123-(4-5+6-7*(89A+B))$	$B-A-9-8*-765+4+321$
5352	09134	$-1+2-(-3-(4567-8+9AB))$	$-B+A-9-87-6-(-5432+1)$
5353	09135	$-12-(-3-4567-8-9AB)$	$-B+A-9-87-6+5432*1$
5354	09136	$1+2+3+4567-8+9AB$	$-B-A9+8+7-(-6-5432)+1$
5355	09137	$-1-(23+4*-56)-(-7*89A-B)$	$-B+A-98+7-6+5432-1$
5356	09138	$-1-234+5678-9A-B$	$-BA+98-76-5432*-1$
5357	09139	$-1*(234-5678+9A+B)$	$-BA+98-76+5432+1$
5358	09140	$-1-2-3+4567+8+9AB$	$B-A9-8-(-7-6)-(-5432+1)$
5359	09141	$12-3+4567-8+9AB$	$-BA-(-9-8-7-(6+5432-1))$
535A	09142	$-12*(34-567+89-(A-B))$	$B-(A9+8+7-(6+5432)+1)$
535B	09143	$1-(-234+5)-(-6-7*(89A-B))$	$-BA-(-9-8)-(-7-6-5432-1)$
5360	09144	$1-23*-4+5-6*7*(-89-A*B)$	$B-A9-8*(-7+6)+5432*1$
5361	09145	$-1-234+5678+9-AB$	$-B-A+9-(87-6+5432*-1)$
5362	09146	$1-(-2+3-4567-8-9AB)$	$-B+A-9-87+6+5432-1$
5363	09147	$12+3+4567-8+9AB$	$-B-A+987*6+543+2+1$
5364	09148	$1+2-3*4*(56+78*9)-A+B$	$-B+A9+(8+7)*(-6-(5-(432-1)))$
5365	09149	$-1+23+4-(-5-6)*(-78*-9-A+B)$	$-B-A9-8+7*6+5432+1$
5366	09150	$1-(234-5678+9)+A*-B$	$BA-98*7*(-6-5)+43+21$
5367	09151	$-1+234+5+6+7*(89A-B)$	$B-A*(-9-87-(6+543+21))$
5368	09152	$1+2-(-3-4567-(8+9AB))$	$B-A-98+7+6-5432*-1$
5369	09153	$1-(2+345)-(-678-9)*A-B$	$B-A-98+7+6+5432+1$
536A	09154	$-1+2-3*(4-56)-7*(-89A-B)$	$BA-987*6+5+432-1$
536B	09155	$12+34+5-67*(-89-A)+B$	$-BA+98+76*(54+32)+1$
5370	09156	$-1+23-(-4567-(-8+9AB))$	$B-A-(-987*6-5*4*-32)+1$
5371	09157	$12-(3-4567-8)+9AB$	$-B-A9*87-6-(5+4)*321$
5372	09158	$1-(-23-4567)-(8-9AB)$	$BA9-8+7-(-65-4321)$
5373	09159	$-1-2345-(67-89A)*B$	$BA9-8-(-76+5-4321)$
5374	09160	$-1-(234-5678)-(9A-B)$	$-B-A+9+8-76+5432*1$
5375	09161	$-12+345+67*(8-9)*A*-B$	$-B-(-A9+87)-(-6+5*4*-321)$
5376	09162	$1-234+5678-9A+B$	$-B-A+9*-8-(-7+6)*5432+1$
5377	09163	$123+4567+89A+B$	$-B-(-A-9+8+76-5432+1)$
5378	09164	$-1*2*(-3456+789+AB)$	$B+A9+8*(765+4+32+1)$
5379	09165	$1-2*(-3456+789+AB)$	$B-(A-9)-(8+76-(5432-1))$
537A	09166	$1+2-3*-4567-89A*B$	$B-A+9-87+6+5432-1$
537B	09167	$123-4*(5-678-9A*B)$	$B-A-(-9+8+76-5432)+1$
5380	09168	$1-(234-5678-9)-A*B$	$B-A+9-87+6-(-5432-1)$
5381	09169	$-1234-5+6-78*(9-AB)$	$BA-9*(87-654-(-3-21))$
5382	09170	$-12*(-3-456+7-8-9)*(-A+B)$	$-B-A*(-9+8)*7-(-6*-543*-2+1)$
5383	09171	$1+23-(-4*56+7*-89A)-B$	$B-(-A+98-7-6-5432+1)$
5384	09172	$-1+23-(-4567-(8+9AB))$	$B-(-A+98-7-6-5432*1)$
5385	09173	$1*23+4567+8+9AB$	$B+A-(98-(7+6))-5432+1))$
5386	09174	$1+23+4567+8+9AB$	$BA9+87-6-5+4321$
5387	09175	$1*2+3-(-4*5+6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA9+8+76-5+4321$
5388	09176	$1-2+34*5*6-(7+8*9A*-B)$	$-BA+9*8-7-6*-543*2+1$
5389	09177	$1+2+3*4*5-6*(-78-9AB)$	$-B-A-(-9-8)-(76*(-54-32)-1)$
538A	09178	$1-(234-56-7)+8*-9*-AB$	$B-A*-9*87-65-43+21$
538B	09179	$12-3*-4+5+6-7*(-8+9A*-B)$	$B-A*9-(8-7-6)-(-5432+1)$
5390	09180	$-1*-23*(-456+789-AB)$	$B-(A+98-(-7*-6+5432-1))$
5391	09181	$1+23*4*(56-7-89+AB)$	$B-(A-9-8+76)+5432-1$
5392	09182	$123+4*(5+6)-7*(-89A-B)$	$B-A+9+8-76+5432*1$
5393	09183	$-123-4+5-67-8*-9*AB$	$B+A-987*-6+543-(2+1)$
5394	09184	$1+234*-5-67*(-8-(9A+B))$	$-BA-9-(8-76-5432+1)$
5395	09185	$-12-34+(-5-6)*78*9+AB$	$B+A+9-8-76+5432-1$
5396	09186	$1234-5-(6+7-8)*-9AB$	$BA9-(-87-6+5-4321)$
5397	09187	$-1-234+5-(-67-8*9*AB)$	$B-(A9-8)-(-7*6-(5432+1))$
5398	09188	$123+4567-(-8+9A*-B)$	$B+A+987*6+543-2*-1$
5399	09189	$1-(-2-345)-67*(8-9A)+B$	$BA-98-76+5432-1$
539A	09190	$1-(234-5678)-9*A+B$	$B-(-A+9*8)-(-7+6)+5432*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
539B	09191	-12 - (-3+456+78*(-9A+B))	BA - (98+76-5432)+1
53A0	09192	-123+4-56-7+8*9* - AB	- B-A98+7-6*54*(3+21)
53A1	09193	-1 - (-23-45)+6*(78+9AB)	BA9+8*(7+654)-3+2+1
53A2	09194	(1/2-3+4^5+6^(7-8))*9+A-B	BA+9-87+6-5*4*321
53A3	09195	-1+2 - (3+45*6+7*89A+B)	B+A9*8*7+(6+54)*(3+21)
53A4	09196	-12+3-4+5*(-67-89)*-A+B	- B-A9-8-(76+5432)*-1
53A5	09197	-1-2+3+45*6+7*89A-B	- B-A9-8-(-76-5432)+1
53A6	09198	-12*(-3-456-(7-89)+A*-B)	- B-A*9*87-(6+5*4)+3*-21
53A7	09199	(1+2)*3*4^5-6+7-8-9+A-B	- BA-9-(-87+6-5432+1)
53A8	09200	-1*-2*34*5*(-6+7-(8-9-A)+B)	- BA-(9-8)+76-(-5432+1)
53A9	09201	-1+2 - (-3-45*6-7*89A)-B	B+A+9+8-76+5432-1
53AA	09202	-1-2*-3*(4^5+6-7*8*9)+A-B	- BA-(9-8)+76+5432+1
53AB	09203	-1-2*-3-4*5 - (-678+9A)*B	- BA+9-8+76+5432*1
53B0	09204	123-4-5*67+8*9*AB	- BA-(-9-(-8+76)-5432-1)
53B1	09205	-1-(23+45+6)-78*(9+A*-B)	BA-98+76*(54+32)-1
53B2	09206	-12-(-345-678*9-AB)	- B-(A+98-76-5432)-1
53B3	09207	-1*(23+4)*(56-78+9-A)*B	- B-A-98-(-76+5432*-1)
53B4	09208	1+234+56+7*(89A-B)	- B+A9+8*(765+43)+2*1
53B5	09209	-123-(45+6)+7+8*9*AB	BA+9+8-76+5*4*321
53B6	09210	-1+234*5+6-78*9A-B	- B-A9+87-6-(-5432+1)
53B7	09211	12+3-4+(56+7)*(89+A+B)	- B-(A9-8-76)+5432-1
53B8	09212	-12*(3-(456-(7+89)+AB))	- B-(A9-(8+76-5432*-1))
53B9	09213	12+345+678*9-A*-B	- BA-9+87+6+5432+1
53BA	09214	-12-34*56-78*(-9A-B)	- BA+98-(7+6-5432+1)
53BB	09215	1-2-(3+4)-(-5-(678-9A)*B)	BA9+87-6*5+4321
5400	09216	1+(2+3-4-5+6)^7*8*9+A-B	- BA+98-(7+6-5432)+1
5401	09217	-1+234-(5+6)-(-7*89A-B)	B-A9-8+76+5432-1
5402	09218	1-23+4+56*(7+8)*(9+AB)	- B*(A9-(8+76+5432))*1
5403	09219	1-2+345-678*9-AB	- BA+9+87-(6-(5432+1))
5404	09220	-123-(4-5-6*-7)+8*9*AB	- BA-(-98+7-(-6*543*2+1))
5405	09221	-123-(45-6)-(-7-8*9*-AB)	BA+987-6*(5+43*-21)
5406	09222	-1*(-2-345-678*9-AB)	- BA+9+87+6*543*2*1
5407	09223	1+2-(-345+678*9)+AB	- B+A9+8*(765-4)+321
5408	09224	-1234+56-78*(9-AB)	- B-A9+87-(-6-5432-1)
5409	09225	-1*(23-456)*(-78+9A-B)	- BA+9-(-8*(7+6)+5432*-1)
540A	09226	-1+2*(345-6)+78*9*-A-B	- BA+98-7-(-6-(5432-1))
540B	09227	-12+3+4*5+(-678+9A)*-B	- B+A-(98-76+5432*-1)
5410	09228	1*2*3*(-4*-56-7+89A+B)	- B-(-A+98)-(-76-5432-1)
5411	09229	-1+23*-4*-5-67*(-8+9)*A*-B	B-A-98+76+5432*1
5412	09230	1+2+3+(4^5+6-7)^8*9+A-B	- BA*(9+8)*(76-54-(-32-1))
5413	09231	-1-(-2-3-4)-(-5-(-678+9A)*-B)	- BA+9+87+6+5432+1
5414	09232	-123-4+5678-9*(A+B)	- B+A*9*87-65+43-2+1
5415	09233	-1-23+456*7+89*AB	B+A-9-(-8-7*6-5432-1)
5416	09234	1^2+(-3+4^5+6+7-8)*9+A-B	B-A9+8+76+5432*1
5417	09235	-123+45-67+8*9*AB	B-A9+8+76+5432+1
5418	09236	12345-6-7*89*(-A-B)	- B+A-9-8+7-6+5432-1
5419	09237	12-345*6-(-789+A)*B	BA-(98-7*6)-(-5432+1)
541A	09238	-12+3*4+56*(7+8)*(9+AB)	B-A-9-8+7-6+5432-1
541B	09239	1-234+5678-(9+A)-B	BA-(9-8-7*6)+5*4*321
5420	09240	12*3*(4+5+67-8+9+AB)	B-(A+9+8+7)-(6-5432+1)
5421	09241	-123+4*5*(-6+7)+8*9*AB	- B+A+9-8-7-6-5432*-1
5422	09242	-1+2-3+4-56*(7-8)*(9+AB)	- BA+98-(-7-6-5432)+1
5423	09243	-1-23-(-45+678-9A)*-B	B-A+9-8-7-6-5432*-1
5424	09244	1*23+4-5+(-678+9A)*B	B-A-98*(-7-65+4)-32+1
5425	09245	-1*(2-(34+5))*(-6-(-78-9A)+B)	B-A9+87-(-6-5432*1)
5426	09246	-1+(-2+3*(-4+5*6)*7)*(8+9)+A-B	B-(A9-87-(6+5432))+1
5427	09247	-123+4-5-(6+7)+8*9*-AB	- B-A+9*(8-7)+6-(-5432+1)
5428	09248	-12+34-5*6*-7-8*9*AB	B+A-(98-76-5432+1)
5429	09249	-123+4*5*(678-9AB)	B+A-98-76-5432*-1
542A	09250	1*(-2-3*-4-5)*(-6*-78+9A*B)	- B-A+9-(-8-7+6)+5432-1
542B	09251	1*(234-56-789+A)*-B	- B-A+9+8+7-6-5432*-1
5430	09252	-1*2^3+(4^5+6+7-8)*9+A-B	B-A-9-8+7-(-6-5432)+1
5431	09253	1+23*45-67*(8-9A+B)	BA9-(-8765+4321)
5432	09254	12*(-3+45*6-(-789+AB))	B-A+987-65*43*2*-1
5433	09255	-1-234-(-5678-9A)-B	B-A98+76*5*4*-3*2*1
5434	09256	-1-234-567-8*9A*B	B-(-A+9+8)-(-7-6)-(-5432+1)
5435	09257	-1-234+5678-9A-B	BA9+8*(-7+654-3+21)
5436	09258	1-(2-3+45)-(67+8)*(-9A+B)	- B-A+98-76+5432-1
5437	09259	1-(234-5678+9-A+B)	- BA-98*(-76+5+4)+3+2*1
5438	09260	-12-(-3-45+(678-9A)*-B)	B+A-9+8-7-6+5432-1
5439	09261	1-(234-(5678-9A))+B	B-(-A+9)-(-8+7+6+5432*-1)
543A	09262	-1+23-(4+5*(-6*7-8-9A)*B)	BA9+87+65+4321
543B	09263	-12-34-(-5-6)*7*(-8-(-9A-B))	B-A*9*87*(6-5)+4+3-21
5440	09264	-1*-2*(3456-7-8-9*AB)	- B+A9-(87+6-(5432+1))
5441	09265	-1+2+3-456*7+89*AB	B+A-9+87-6*(-54+3)*21
5442	09266	-12+34-56*(7+8)*(-9-AB)	BA-98-7-6+5432-1
5443	09267	1+2+3-456*7+89*AB	BA-(98+7)-6-5432*-1
5444	09268	1+2*3-(-456*7-89*AB)	BA-98-(7+6-5432-1)
5445	09269	-123+4-(-5-6+7+8*9*-AB)	BA9-87*(-65+4)+32-1
5446	09270	-1*-2*(34+5)*(6-7+89+A-B)	B-A+9+8-(7-6)-(-5432+1)
5447	09271	-12+345+(67-8+9)*A*B	- BA+98+7*6+5432+1
5448	09272	-1-(23+45)-(67+8*-9*AB)	- B+A+9+8-(-7-(-6+5432+1))
5449	09273	1*234+56-7*-89A-B	B-A*-9+8-76-5432*-1
544A	09274	1+234+56+7*89A-B	BA-9-8*-765-(-4-321)
544B	09275	-1+2-3*45-6+7+8*-9*-AB	B-A-98*(-7-65+4)+3*-2*1
5450	09276	-1234-5-(67-8*9AB)	B+A-(-9+8+7-6)-(-5432-1)
5451	09277	-1234-(56+7+8*-9AB)	BA-9-87-(6-5432+1)
5452	09278	12+3-456*7-89*-AB	- BA+9876-(5+4321)
5453	09279	-1-234+5678-9A+B	BA-(9+87)-(-6-5432-1)
5454	09280	1*-234-(-5678+9-(A+B))	B+A*9*87-(65-43-21)
5455	09281	1-234+5678-9A+B	B-A-(-98+76-5432*1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5456	09282	$12^*(345+67-8+9A-B)$	$BA-98-(-7+6-5432-1)$
5457	09283	$-12-3-45-(67-8^*-9^*-AB)$	$B-A^*9+87-(-6-5432+1)$
5458	09284	$-12-3^*456+78^*(-9+AB)$	$B-(-A9+87+6-5432)-1$
5459	09285	$1-2345-6-(78+9)^*-AB$	$BA-98+7-6^*-543^*2^*1$
545A	09286	$-1234+5-(67+8^*-9AB)$	$B-(-A9+87+6-5432)+1$
545B	09287	$-1+2^*(34-5-(67-8))^*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A9^*(876+5^*(-4-32))^*1$
5460	09288	$1^*2^*(3-4+56^*78-9AB)$	$BA-9-8-76+5432-1$
5461	09289	$-123+4+5678-9-AB$	$BA-9-87+6-(-5432+1)$
5462	09290	$123-4^*-56-7^*(-89-A)^*B$	$BA-(9+8-(-76+5432)-1)$
5463	09291	$-1234-56-(-7+8^*-9AB)$	$B-A^*(-987-(-654+321))$
5464	09292	$-123-4+5678-(9A+B)$	$BA-98+7+6+5432-1$
5465	09293	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)+7+8+9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9^*-8-76+5432^*-1)$
5466	09294	$12+34^*(-5-6-(-7-89)+AB)$	$BA-98+7+6-(-5432-1)$
5467	09295	$-1-2345+6+(-78-9)^*-AB$	$B+A9-(876-5432)-1$
5468	09296	$-1+2^*3-456-7^*(8-9AB)$	$B+A9-(87-(6+5432-1))$
5469	09297	$-1-234+5678+9+A+B$	$B+A9-87+6-5432^*-1$
546A	09298	$-1^*(234-(5678+9)-(A+B))$	$-BA9-(87-6543)-21$
546B	09299	$-1234+5+6789-AB$	$BA-(-9+87)-(6^*-543^*2+1)$
5470	09300	$-123+4-(-5678+9A)-B$	$-BA9-(-8-7)-6^*(-5-4^*321)$
5471	09301	$123-(-4567+8-9AB)$	$B+A-9-8-7^*-6+5432+1$
5472	09302	$1-(2-3)-(45+67-8^*9^*AB)$	$B+A^*-9^*-87-6+54-32+1$
5473	09303	$-1+(2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*-5+6)^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A^*-9^*-8^*(-7-6)-5-(-4-32+1)$
5474	09304	$-12-34+5-67-8^*9^*-AB$	$BA-9+8-76+5432-1$
5475	09305	$1^*-2-3-(-4-56)^*(7+89+A+B)$	$BA-9+8-76-5432^*-1$
5476	09306	$123+4-5-6+7^*(8-9A^*-B)$	$BA+9-(8+76-(5432-1))$
5477	09307	$-123+4+5678+9-AB$	$BA-(-9+87-(6-(-5432+1)))$
5478	09308	$12+3-456-7^*(8-9AB)$	$-B+A9+8-(-7^*6+5^*4^*-321)$
5479	09309	$1-23^*-4^*(5+67)+89+AB$	$BA+9-87+6+5432+1$
547A	09310	$-1234-5-(-6789-A^*-B)$	$B+A+(-9+87^{\wedge}6)/(5+4/3)/2+1$
547B	09311	$-1-2-(-3-(4^{\wedge}5+(-6+7)^*8))^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A9-8)-(76-5432+1)$
5480	09312	$-1^*-2^*3^*4^*(-567-(-8-9^*AB))$	$B+A9+8-76+5432^*1$
5481	09313	$1+23-(-4+5)-6+78^*(-9-A^*-B)$	$-B+A9+8^*7-6+5432+1$
5482	09314	$1-2+3^*-45-(6^*-7-8^*9^*AB)$	$B-A+9+8-7^*-6-5432^*-1$
5483	09315	$-123-(-45+6-(7-8^*9^*-AB))$	$B+A^*9^*87+65-4-32-1$
5484	09316	$-123-4-(-56-(-7+8^*9^*AB))$	$B+A-9-8^*-7-6+5432^*1$
5485	09317	$123+4567+8+9AB$	$-BA9^*(8+765-43+21)$
5486	09318	$12+345+6+7^*(89A-B)$	$B+A9-8^*(765-(43+21))$
5487	09319	$1^*2^{\wedge}3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6+(7+8)^*9)+A-B$	$-BA98-(-76-5432)+1$
5488	09320	$-1234+5-(-6789-A^*-B)$	$-BA9-87-(-6543+2+1)$
5489	09321	$-1^*2-(-3-4^{\wedge}5+6-(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$BA-98+7^*6+5432-1$
548A	09322	$-123+4+5678-9A+B$	$BA+9-(-8+76-5432+1)$
548B	09323	$-1234-(-5-6^*-7)-8^*-9AB$	$BA-(-9-8+76-5432^*1)$
5490	09324	$-12^*(3-456-7-8+9-A-B)$	$BA+9+8-76+5432+1$
5491	09325	$1^*2-(-3-4^{\wedge}5+6-(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-BA9-87+6543-2^*-1$
5492	09326	$-1+2-3-45^*(6-7^*(-89+AB))$	$-BA9-87+6543+2+1$
5493	09327	$1234+56^*(7+89)-AB$	$-B-A^*-9^*87+65-4-3-2^*1$
5494	09328	$-123+4+5678+9^*-A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6+5432^*1$
5495	09329	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^*4^{\wedge}5+6^*7+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+98^*(7+65-4)+3+21$
5496	09330	$-1^*2^{\wedge}3^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$BA9-(-876-5^*43^*-21)$
5497	09331	$-1-234-(-5-67)^*(8+9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*(7+6)-5)^*(4^*3-2)^{\wedge}1$
5498	09332	$-1-23+(4+5)^*(-6+7-89^*-A-B)$	$BA-987^*-6-(-543-21)$
5499	09333	$1-(-2+3)-(4^*5-(-67+8^*9^*AB))$	$B+A^*9^*87-6-5^*-4+32^*1$
549A	09334	$(-1-2)^*-3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)+7^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9^*876+5-4^*321$
549B	09335	$1^*2-34-56+7-8^*9^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6-(-5432-1)$
54A0	09336	$1-2^*345-67-8^*-9A^*B$	$BA-9-(8+7^*6-5432+1)$
54A1	09337	$-1+(-2^{\wedge}3+4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B-A+9^*-8-(7+65)^*4^*(-3-21)$
54A2	09338	$12^*(3-4-(56+7^*-89-A+B))$	$-B+A9-(-8-7^*-6)-5432^*-1$
54A3	09339	$-12-345-(6+78^*(-9A+B))$	$-B-A+9+8+76+5432-1$
54A4	09340	$1-2+3+(-4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B-A-(-9-87+6)-(-5432-1)$
54A5	09341	$-1-(23+4)-56-(-7+8^*-9^*AB)$	$-B-(-A-9-8-76-5432-1)$
54A6	09342	$-1234-5-6-7+8^*9AB$	$B-A-(9-87)-(6-(5432-1))$
54A7	09343	$1^*2+3+(-4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B+A-9-(-8-76)+5432+1$
54A8	09344	$-12+3-(4+56+7+8^*-9^*AB)$	$B-A-9+87-6+5432+1$
54A9	09345	$12+3+(4+5+67)^*(89-A+B)$	$-B+A-(-98-76)-5^*-4^*321$
54AA	09346	$-12+34^*-5+678^*(9-A+B)$	$B-(-A9-87^*65-43^*21)$
54AB	09347	$12-34-56+7-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B-A+98-7+6+5432-1$
54B0	09348	$1^*2^*(-34+5-6)^*(7-(-8+9A+B))$	$-BA9-87-(-6543-21)$
54B1	09349	$-123-(-4-5-67+8^*-9^*AB)$	$-B-A+98-7+6+5432+1$
54B2	09350	$-1-2-345-(6+78^*(-9A+B))$	$-B^*(-A9-876+54+321)$
54B3	09351	$-12-(345-6+78^*(-9A+B))$	$-B+A9-8-7-6+5432^*1$
54B4	09352	$-1234-(-5+6+7)-8^*-9AB$	$-B+A9-8-7-6+5432+1$
54B5	09353	$((1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^*6)^*7+8^*9+A-B$	$-B+A-9+87+(-6-5432)^*-1$
54B6	09354	$1-23-45-6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$B-A-(9-87-6-5432+1)$
54B7	09355	$12-3-4-5-6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$BA-9-8+76-5^*4^*-321$
54B8	09356	$-1234-5-6+7+8^*9AB$	$B-A-(9-(87+6)-5432+1)$
54B9	09357	$1^*2-34+5^*-6-7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B-A+98-7-6-5432-1$
54BA	09358	$1-2-3-(-4-5)-67-8^*9^*-AB$	$-B+A+9-(-87+6-5432)-1$
54BB	09359	$(-1^*-2+3^{\wedge}4+5+6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B-A-(-98+7+6+5432-1)$
5500	09360	$12+34-56^*(7-8-(9+AB))$	$-B+A-(-98+7)-6^*-543^*-2^*-1$
5501	09361	$1^*234+56+7^*(89A+B)$	$-B-A-(-98-7)-(-6-5432+1)$
5502	09362	$-1-2+3+4+5-6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$B-A+98-7+6^*543^*2^*1$
5503	09363	$-1+23-(45-6^*-7+8^*-9^*AB)$	$B+A98^*7-(-6+54)^*(-3+21)$
5504	09364	$-1-(-234-5^*-67+8^*-9^*AB)$	$-B+A98+76^*5+4321$
5505	09365	$-1234+5-(-6+7)^*8^*-9AB$	$B+A+9-8+76+5432-1$
5506	09366	$12^*(-3+4)^*(567-8-(-9+AB))$	$BA-9-8-7-6+5432^*1$
5507	09367	$12-345-6-78^*(-9A+B)$	$BA-(9+8-(-7-(6-5432-1)))$
5508	09368	$1+2+3+4+5+6+78^*(9^*A+B)$	$-B+A9+8-7-6+5432+1$
5509	09369	$-123-4^*5-678^*(-9-(-A+B))$	$BA-98+76+5432-1$
550A	09370	$-1^*2^*(-34-(-56^*-78-9AB))$	$-B+A+9+87-(-6-5432+1)$
550B	09371	$123-4^*(-56-7-(-8-9)^*-AB)$	$B+A^*(98-76)^*(54-3-21)$
5510	09372	$1+2^*(3-4)-56-(-7+8^*9^*-AB)$	$-B^*(A-(987+65)+432)^*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5511	09373	$-1-2*3-45-6+7+8*-9*-AB$	$B-A+9+87+6-5432*-1$
5512	09374	$-1-234+5678+9A-B$	$B-A+9+87+6+5432+1$
5513	09375	$-1-(-2+3-(4-56))+7+8*9*AB$	$B-A98-7*-6*5*(43+2-1)$
5514	09376	$1-(234-5678)-(-9A+B)$	$-B-(-A9+8-7-6-5432+1)$
5515	09377	$-12-3-(-4-5-(6-78))* (9-AB)$	$B+A+98-7-(6-5432+1)$
5516	09378	$-12+345+6-7*-89A+B$	$-B-(-A9+8)+7+6+5432+1$
5517	09379	$1*2+(-3+4^5+6+7+8)*9+A-B$	$BA-9-8+7-6+5432-1$
5518	09380	$1+2-(3+45+6)-(-7-8*9*AB)$	$BA-(9+8)-((7-6)*-5432-1)$
5519	09381	$-123+4*(5+678+9AB)$	$-B+A9+8+7-6+5432*1$
551A	09382	$1-2+(-3+4+5^6/(7+8))*9+A-B$	$-B+A9-(-8-7+6-5432)+1$
551B	09383	$1+2+345-6+7*89A+B$	$-B*(A-98-(7-6+543)+21)$
5520	09384	$12-(-345-6)-7*-89A-B$	$BA+9-8-7-(6+5432*-1)$
5521	09385	$-1-(2-34)-(-5+67+8*9*-AB)$	$B+A*9*87-(-6+5-43)*-2*-1$
5522	09386	$1-(-2-3)-(-45-(6+7))-8*9*-AB$	$B+A9-8-7+6+5432+1$
5523	09387	$1-2-(-34+5+67)-8*-9*AB$	$B+A9-8+7-6-5432*-1$
5524	09388	$1-2*34+5678-9A-B$	$B+A9+8-(7+6-5432+1)$
5525	09389	$-1-(234-5678)-9+AB$	$B+A9-(-8+7)-6-5432*-1$
5526	09390	$-1+2-3-(45-6)-(-7+8*9*-AB)$	$B+A9+8-(7+6)-(-5432-1)$
5527	09391	$1-234+5678-9+AB$	$B-(-A-98-7)-(6-5432+1)$
5528	09392	$12-3*-4567+89*-AB$	$BA-9-8+7+6-5432*-1$
5529	09393	$-1-23-45-6*-7-8*-9*AB$	$BA-(9+8-7-(6+5432)-1)$
552A	09394	$1+2-3*-4*567-8-9*(A+B)$	$-B*(A-9-87-6-(543-21))$
552B	09395	$12+3-45+6-7+8*9*AB$	$BA+987-65*-43*-2*-1$
5530	09396	$-1-(234-5678)-(-9A-B)$	$BA+9-8-(-7-(-6-5432))*-1$
5531	09397	$1+23-4-56+7-8*9*-AB$	$BA-(9-8)-(-7+6-5432)+1$
5532	09398	$1-234+5678+9A+B$	$B-(-A9+8)-(-7-6-5432)-1$
5533	09399	$-1+2*(-34+5*(678-9-A+B))$	$-B-A-(-9876-(-5-4321))$
5534	09400	$-1-2-(3-45+67+8*-9*AB)$	$BA-(-9-87-6+5*4*-321)$
5535	09401	$-1+2-3-4+5678+9*(-A-B)$	$BA-(-9-8+7+6-5432-1)$
5536	09402	$-12-34+5678-9-AB$	$-BA9+8-7+6+543-21$
5537	09403	$-1+234-56+7*(8-9A*-B)$	$-BA-9*8*-76+5*(432-1)$
5538	09404	$-12-3456-(7-89AB)$	$B-A-9*(-8-765+43)+21$
5539	09405	$123*(4-(-56-7-8))-(-9A+B)$	$B*(-A9-8*76-(5-4+3+2))*-1$
553A	09406	$1+2+3-4*(-5+6+7)+8*9*AB$	$-B+A9-8-7*-6+5432*1$
553B	09407	$-1-(2345+6-789A+B)$	$B+A9-(-8-7+6*543*2*-1)$
5540	09408	$12*-3*(4-5+6+7*(-8-9))-A*B$	$-B+A987-6-5432*1$
5541	09409	$1-2345-(6-(789A-B))$	$-B-(-A987-(-6-5432)-1)$
5542	09410	$-123-4-567+8*-9A*-B$	$-BA9-8-7*-6*5*(43+2)+1$
5543	09411	$-1234-5-678*(9-A-B)$	$-B+A9-8*-765-(-432+1)$
5544	09412	$-123-4+5678+9*(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8*765-432*-1$
5545	09413	$12345-6-7-89AB$	$BA-(-9-8-7+6-5432+1)$
5546	09414	$12-(34+5-6)-(-7+8*9*-AB)$	$-BA9-8-7+6+543+2+1$
5547	09415	$-1-2-3456-7+89AB$	$BA-(-9-8)-(-7+6-5432)+1$
5548	09416	$-1*2*(34-(5+6))-(-7-8))*(-9A+B)$	$-BA9+8+7+6+543-21$
5549	09417	$-1-(-2+34-5678)-(-9+AB)$	$BA98-7-6543-2+1$
554A	09418	$-12-3456+7+89AB$	$BA98-7-6543*(2-1)$
554B	09419	$-1234-5-(-6789-A+B)$	$BA98-7-6543-(-2+1)$
5550	09420	$-12-34+5678+9-AB$	$BA98-7-6543+2*1$
5551	09421	$-1234-5+6789-A+B$	$B-A-(-9876+5)-4321$
5552	09422	$12*(-3+4-(-567+8+9+A*B))$	$-B+A9+8-7*-6+5432*1$
5553	09423	$-12-(34-(5678-9+A*-B))$	$BA+98-76+5432+1$
5554	09424	$-1-2-34+5678-9A-B$	$-BA9-(-8+7-6543-(-2-1))$
5555	09425	$12345+6-7-89AB$	$BA-98*(-7-65)-(-4+321)$
5556	09426	$1-23-(4-5678+9+AB)$	$-BA9-(-8-(-7+6543))-2+1$
5557	09427	$1234-56-7*(-8+9A-B)$	$BA-(-9-8-(7+6-(-5432-1)))$
5558	09428	$1*-2-3-(4+5*(6-7))+8*9*-AB$	$B-(-A9-(-8+7*6))+5432*1$
5559	09429	$-1234-(-5-6789)+A-B$	$-BA9+8-7+6+543-2*-1$
555A	09430	$12-34+5678-9-AB$	$BA98+7-6543+2*-1$
555B	09431	$1+23-456-7*(-8-9AB)$	$BA98+7-6543-2+1$
5560	09432	$12-3456-7+89AB$	$BA98+7+6543*(-2+1)$
5561	09433	$-12+3-(-4+5-6-7)-8*9*-AB$	$BA98+7-(6543-2)-1$
5562	09434	$1-23+4+5678-9-AB$	$BA98-(-7+6543-2*1)$
5563	09435	$-12-34+5678-(9A-B)$	$BA98+7-6543+2+1$
5564	09436	$-12*(-3-4-(5678+9-AB))$	$-BA9-(8+7-6543)+21$
5565	09437	$1-23-(4-5678)-(-9A+B)$	$B+A987-6*543*2-1$
5566	09438	$-12-3-(-456-7*(89A-B))$	$B-A+98+76+5432-1$
5567	09439	$12345+6+7-89AB$	$B+A987-6*543*2+1$
5568	09440	$-1-2-(-3+(-45+6+7))*(89+AB))$	$-BA9-(-8-7-(6543-2))+1$
5569	09441	$-123+4-(-5678+9-A-B)$	$B-(-A-9876)-(-5+4321)$
556A	09442	$-1*(2345-6-789A-B)$	$-BA9+8-(-7-6543-2+1)$
556B	09443	$1-(-2+3*4*-5678)-(-9+AB)$	$BA98-7-6543+21$
5570	09444	$1+2345+6*7*(-8+9)*AB$	$-BA9+8-(-7-6543)-(-2-1)$
5571	09445	$1-23+4+5678-(9A+B)$	$BA+9+8*765+432*1$
5572	09446	$-1-(2+34-(5678-9A+B))$	$BA+9-8*-765-(-432-1)$
5573	09447	$-12-(-3+45-67)+8*-9*-AB$	$B+A+(9*8+7+6^5)/(4/3-2^8-1)$
5574	09448	$12-34+5678-(-9+AB)$	$B+A9+8*7+6*-543*2*-1$
5575	09449	$-12+3+4+5678-(9+AB)$	$-B*(-A-(9+8*76))+5*(4-3-21))$
5576	09450	$-1-23-(-4-5678)-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9*(8+7)-65*4*(-32+1)$
5577	09451	$-1234+5-(-6789-A-B)$	$B+A-(-9876-5+4321)$
5578	09452	$1-(-2+34)-(-5678+9A-B)$	$-BA9+8-7+6+543+21$
5579	09453	$-1+2*-3*4*5*-6+7+89-AB$	$-B+A98-7*-65+4321$
557A	09454	$-12+3*4+5678-(9+AB)$	$-B-(-A9+8)-(-76+5432*-1)$
557B	09455	$12-3-(-4-(-5+6+7))+8*9*AB$	$-B+A9-8+76+5432+1$
5580	09456	$1*(2+3-4)*5678-9-AB$	$BA+9-(-8-7*6)+5432+1$
5581	09457	$-1-(23+4-(5678-9A))+B$	$BA98+7-(6543-21)$
5582	09458	$-1*(-2+3)* (45-67+8*9*-AB)$	$-B+A-9*(8+7)*(-6-54)+3*(2+1)$
5583	09459	$-123-(-4-5678-(9+A+B))$	$B+A9*(8-7+65)+432*-1$
5584	09460	$-12-(-3-(4+5678)+9A)-B$	$B-(-A-98)+76+5432-1$
5585	09461	$-1+2-3-4+5678-9A-B$	$-BA-9*(-8-765-(-43+21))$
5586	09462	$1-2+3+4+5678-9-AB$	$B-(-A-(98+76))+5432+1$
5587	09463	$12-34-(-5678+9A-B)$	$BA9-87+65*43*2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5588	09464	$-12*(-345-6*7*8-9A-B)$	$-B(-A-9+8+7*(-65-43*21))$
5589	09465	$-1-(23-4-5678)-9A+B$	$B+A*9+87-(-6-(5432+1))$
558A	09466	$12-3+456+7*(89A-B)$	$BA-9*-8-7+6-(-5432+1)$
558B	09467	12345-67-89AB	$BA-9*-8-(7-6)*-5432-1$
5590	09468	$12345-6*-7-89AB$	$B-A+(-98-7)*-65-4*(3-2)*1$
5591	09469	$12-(-3+4-5678+9+AB)$	$-B+A9+8+76+5432-1$
5592	09470	$-1-2+3-4+5678+9-AB$	$-B+A9+87-6+5432+1$
5593	09471	$-1-2+3+4+5678-9A-B$	$-B+A9-(-8-(76+5432+1))$
5594	09472	$-12+3*4+5678-(-9+AB)$	$-B+A9+87+6*543*2-1$
5595	09473	$1-2+3+4+5678-9A-B$	$B+A+9-8+(-7-6)*((-5-4)^3+2)*1$
5596	09474	$12-3-4+5678-9A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7*-6-5*4^3)*2+1$
5597	09475	$-1+2*3-4+5678+9-AB$	$-B+A9*8+765+4321$
5598	09476	$1+2-(-3+4-5678-9+AB)$	$B-(-A9+8-(76-5432*-1))$
5599	09477	$12+3-(-4-5678+9+AB)$	$B+A9-8+76+5432+1$
559A	09478	$-1+2-(-34-5678-9*-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8*7+6^5+(4*3)^(2+1)$
559B	09479	$-1+2-(-3+4-5-6*7+8*-9*AB)$	$-B+A*-9*(-87+6)-5*-4*32*1$
559A0	09480	$-1*(2-(-3-4)-5678+9A-B)$	$-B+A9-(-87-6-5432+1)$
55A1	09481	$1-2-3-4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+98+76-5432*-1$
55A2	09482	$-12+3+4+5678-(9+AB)$	$-B-(-A9-87)-(-6-(5432+1))$
55A3	09483	$1-2-(-3-4-5678)-(-9-A*-B)$	$BA-9-(-87+6-5432+1)$
55A4	09484	$1+2+3-(-4-5678)+9-AB$	$BA-9+8+76+5432-1$
55A5	09485	$1-2+3*4+5678+9-AB$	$BA-9-(-87+6)-(-5432-1)$
55A6	09486	$-1*-2*3*(-4+56+78+9AB)$	$BA-9+8+76+5432+1$
55A7	09487	$1-2+3-4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A*-9*(-87+6)-(-543+21)$
55A8	09488	$1-(-23-4-5678)-9-AB$	$BA+9-8+76+5432+1$
55A9	09489	$-1+2-(-3+4)+5678-(9A-B)$	$-B+A*(98-(7+6*54)+321)$
55AA	09490	$1*(2-(-3+4))*56+7*(8-9+AB)$	$BA-98+7*(65+43*21)$
55AB	09491	$1+23-4+5678-9A-B$	$B+A9+8+76+5432-1$
55B0	09492	$1*2*(-3-4)*(-567-8+9A+B)$	$B+A9-(-8-76)+5432*1$
55B1	09493	$-12-(-34-5678+9A+B)$	$B+A9+8-(-76-5432)+1$
55B2	09494	$12-3+(-45-67)*-8*9-A-B$	$-BA+9*876-543*2*-1$
55B3	09495	$1-2+34-(-5678+9)-AB$	$BA-9+87+6+5432-1$
55B4	09496	$-1+23-(-4-5678)-(9-AB)$	$-B-A98*-7-654-321$
55B5	09497	$-1+2+3+4+5678-9-AB$	$B+A9*8+765+4321$
55B6	09498	$-123+4+5+6-(-7-89*-A*-B)$	$BA+98-7-6+5432-1$
55B7	09499	$123-45*(67-89+A)*B$	$BA+98-7-6+5432*1$
55B8	09500	$1-234-5*-67-8*-9*AB$	$BA+98-7-(6-5432-1)$
55B9	09501	$1-(23-45)-(-6*7+8*9*-AB)$	$BA+9-(-87-(-6+5432-1))$
55BA	09502	$-1+2+3*4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A9+87-(-6-5432+1)$
55BB	09503	$-12+3+4+5678-9-A*B$	$BA+9+8+76-5432*-1$
5600	09504	$-1+23-(-4-(5678+9-AB))$	$BA+9-(-8-(76+5432+1))$
5601	09505	$-1*(2-(34+5678)-(-9A-B))$	$B-A-9*-8*(76+54+3-21)$
5602	09506	$1+23-(-4-5678-9+AB)$	$B+A+(9*8+7)*6*5*4+3+2*1$
5603	09507	$1-(-2-3)-(-4*5+(-678+9)*A-B)$	$-BA9+8*7+6543+21$
5604	09508	$-1+2-3*-4+5678+9*-A-B$	$-BA+9*(-8+765)-4-32-1$
5605	09509	$1-(-23-4-5678+9+A*B)$	$BA+9-8*(-7-6)-5432*-1$
5606	09510	$1+2-(-34-5678)-(-9A+B)$	$BA+98-7+6+5432-1$
5607	09511	$-1+23-(-4-5678+9A-B)$	$BA+98-(-7+6)*5432-1$
5608	09512	$1-(-2-3)-(-4+5)+67-8*-9*AB$	$BA+98-7+6+5432+1$
5609	09513	$1+23-4+5678-(9A-B)$	$BA+98-(-7+6+5432*-1)$
560A	09514	$1-(23-4*-5)+678*(9-(A-B))$	$BA*(98-(7+65)-(-4-32-1))$
560B	09515	$1+23-(-4-56+7)-8*-9*AB$	$B*(-A9+87+654-(32-1))$
5610	09516	$12+3+4+5678+9-A*B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6)*(5+4)^3+2-1$
5611	09517	$-1+23-4+5678+9-A*B$	$BA-(-98-7+6*-543*2*1)$
5612	09518	$-1+2-(-34-5678-(-9-A*B))$	$B+A98*7-654-321$
5613	09519	$1-23*4+5678+9-(-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^5+(4*3)^(2+1)$
5614	09520	$123-4*(-56+78)*9*-A-B$	$-BA+9*(-8+765+4)+3-2*-1$
5615	09521	$12+3+4+5678-9A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7-6)*(-5*4-3^A-2-1)$
5616	09522	$123+45+6+78*(-9-A*-B)$	$-B+A987-6+5*-4*321$
5617	09523	$12-(-345+6)-7*(8-9A*B)$	$B+A-9+8-(-7-6)*((5+4)^3+2)*1$
5618	09524	$1*-2-3+4+5678-9-A-B$	$B+A*(98-76)-(-5432+1)$
5619	09525	$-1+23+4-(-5678+9*A)-B$	$B+A*987-6*(543-21)$
561A	09526	$-1-23+4+5+6-78*(-9A+B)$	$-BA9+87-(-6543-(-2-1))$
561B	09527	$1+23+4-(-5678-9)-A*B$	$-BA9-(-87-6543-2*-1)$
5620	09528	$1-(2-34)+5678-(9A-B)$	$-BA9+87+6543-2+1$
5621	09529	$1+2*-3*-4-56*(-7-8-9A-B)$	$-BA9+87+6543*(2-1)$
5622	09530	$-12-34-(-5678-9A+B)$	$-BA9-(-87-6543-2+1)$
5623	09531	$-12-34-567+8*9A*B$	$-BA9-(-87-6543+2*-1)$
5624	09532	$-12-34+5678-9A-B$	$-BA9+87+6543+2+1$
5625	09533	$-1+2*-3-45*6*(78+9-AB)$	$B+A-9*8+7*(6*5+4+3)^2+1$
5626	09534	$1*-2*-3*(4+56+78+9AB)$	$-B+A987+6*5*-4*-321$
5627	09535	$-1+2*(3456-789)-A*-B$	$B-A98*7+654*(-3+21)$
5628	09536	$1-23-4+5678-9-(-A-B)$	$-BA-9*-876+5*4*3*2-1$
5629	09537	$-1+2*34*(5+6+78)+9A*B$	$B*(-A+9)*8+7-6*(-5-4*-32*1)$
562A	09538	$1+2+3+4+5678-9*A-B$	$BA+98*(76+5+4*-3-2*1)$
562B	09539	$12-34+5-678*(-9A-B)$	$B+A+9-(-8-7)*(6+5^4+3)-(-2-1)$
5630	09540	$-1234-(-5-6789)-A*-B$	$-B-A98-7+6543-21$
5631	09541	$-1+2-3-(-456-7*89A-B)$	$BA+98*(76-5)-(-4+321)$
5632	09542	$-1-2-34-567+8*9A*B$	$BA9-87*-65+43*2*1$
5633	09543	$12+3+4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+9*8*(7+6*5^4-3)^2*1$
5634	09544	$1-(23-(4+5678-9))-(-A+B)$	$B+A987-6-5*4*321$
5635	09545	$-1-2-3+4+5678-9-A+B$	$BA+9*(8+765-43)+21$
5636	09546	$-123+4+5+6+7*(-8-9A)*-B$	$B+A-9*8-7*((6+5*-4)^3/2+1)$
5637	09547	$1+2-3+4+5678+9-A-B$	$-B-A9-8-7*(-654-321)$
5638	09548	$1+23-(-4-5-67)+8*9*AB$	$B*(-A9+8+76)*(-5+4)*(3+21)$
5639	09549	$-1+2-34-(-5678+9+A-B)$	$-BA+98*(7+65)-(-43+2)*1$
563A	09550	$123-45-(6-7)*8*9*AB$	$B+A+9+8*7*(6*5+4)*(3+2)*1$
563B	09551	$12+3*4*567+8*-9A+B$	$BA-(-9+8)-(-7+65)*4*(-3-21)$
5640	09552	$-1-23-(4-(5678+9-A-B))$	$-BA-98*-76-543+21$
5641	09553	$-12-3*-4*567*(-8+9)-A-B$	$B+A-9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3/2*1$
5642	09554	$12-3*45*6*((-7+8)*-9A-B)$	$-BA9+87-(-6543-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5643	09555	$1+2*34 - (-5678-9)-AB$	$B+A+((-9-8)^*-7+6*5)*4^3-2*1$
5644	09556	$1-23-(4-5678+9-(A-B))$	$B+A987+6+5^*-4*321$
5645	09557	$-1234+56+7+89A^*-B$	$B-A9*(8-(7-6+5))-(43+21))$
5646	09558	$-123-(4-5678-9A)+B$	$B-A9*(8-7+6+5)-(43+21))$
5647	09559	$-12-3*4-567+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B-A9*(8-7+6+5)-(43+21))$
5648	09560	$12-34-(-5678-(-9+A)))-B$	$B*(A+987^*-6-(-5432+1))$
5649	09561	$-1234+5+6789+AB$	$B+A-987-6*(5-4*321)$
564A	09562	$12-34+5678-9-A+B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7+6)*5^*-4/3^A-2^A1$
564B	09563	$1-2-(34-5678)-(-9-A+B)$	$BA+9876-(5+4321)$
5650	09564	$1-(2+3)-(45*67+89^*-AB)$	$-B-(A98+7)-(-6543+2*1)$
5651	09565	$1234+56*78+9AB$	$-B-A98-7+6543-2+1$
5652	09566	$-1-(-2-3+4-5678+9+A+B)$	$-B-(A98+7-6543*(2-1))$
5653	09567	$-12-3-4+5678-9-A+B$	$BA9-8-(-7+65^*-43^*-2^*-1)$
5654	09568	$-1-2+3+45^*-67-89^*-AB$	$-B-(A98+7)-(-6543+2^*-1)$
5655	09569	$-123+4+5678+9+AB$	$-B-A98-7+6543-(-2-1)$
5656	09570	$-12-(-3+4-(-567-8*9A^*-B))$	$B-A9-(8+7*(-654-321))$
5657	09571	$-12+3-4+5678-(9-A)-B$	$B^*-A*(-9-(8-7)-65)-(-4-(-3-2+1))$
5658	09572	$1-(2-3-4)-(-5678-(-9-A)+B)$	$B+A+9-(-8-7)*(6+5^A+3+2)+1$
5659	09573	$12-(3+4)+5678-(9+A+B)$	$BA+9876+5-4321$
565A	09574	$1-23-4*5^*-6*(78-9+A+B)$	$-BA-987+6543-21$
565B	09575	$12-3+4+567-8*9^*-AB$	$-B-A*98-7-6*54*(3+21)$
5660	09576	$1-23-4-(-5678-9)-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)*((-7^*-6+5)^*-4*3+2^A1)$
5661	09577	$123+45-67+8*9^*AB$	$-B-A98-(-7-6543)-(-2+1)$
5662	09578	$1-23-4+5678-9+A+B$	$-B-A98+7+6543+2^*-1$
5663	09579	$-12+3+4+5678-9+A-B$	$-B-A98-(-7-6543)-(-2-1)$
5664	09580	$1-2-3-4+5678-9-A+B$	$-B-A98+7-6543*(2+1)$
5665	09581	$-12+3-(-4-5678+9+A-B)$	$-B-A98+7+6543+2-1$
5666	09582	$12-(34-5678+9-A-B)$	$-B-(A98-7-6543)-2^*-1$
5667	09583	$-12-3-4+5678+9+A-B$	$-B-A98-(-7-6543)+2+1$
5668	09584	$-1-2-(-3+4-5678+9-(-A+B))$	$BA9+8+7+65*43^*2+1$
5669	09585	$1-(2+3-4)-(567-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$BA98+76*(54-3)^*2^*-1$
566A	09586	$-1+2-(3-4-5678-9+A+B)$	$B-A98-7+6543-2*1$
566B	09587	$1-(23-4*5^*-6^*-78+9AB)$	$B-A98-(7-6543+2-1)$
5670	09588	$1+2+3-4+5678-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7*(6^*5+4+3)^A2^*1$
5671	09589	$1+2-34-(-5678-9-A-B)$	$B-A98-7+6543+2-1$
5672	09590	$1+2-(3-4)-(5678-9-(-A+B))$	$-B-A^*-9*8+6*(5+43-2+1)$
5673	09591	$-12-(3-4-5678-9-A+B)$	$B-(A98+7-6543-2-1)$
5674	09592	$1-2+3-(-4-5678+9-A)-B$	$BA9-87^*-65-(43+2)^*1$
5675	09593	$-1-23-45*(-67-89)-AB$	$-B*(-A98-7+65-432^*-1)$
5676	09594	$-1-2+3+4+5678-9-A+B$	$B+A-9+(-8^*-7+6+5)*((-4^*-3)^A2-1)$
5677	09595	$1-(-2-3)-(-4+567-8*9A^*B)$	$-BA+9*(87+654)+321$
5678	09596	$1+23+45^*-67+89^*AB$	$-BA-987+6543-(2+1)$
5679	09597	$-1*(2-3+4-567+89)*(A+B)$	$-BA-987-(-6543+2)^*1$
567A	09598	$1-2+3^*-4*(-567+8-9)+A-B$	$-BA-987+6543-2+1$
567B	09599	$-12+3+4+5678+9-A+B$	$B-A98-(-7-6543+2+1)$
5680	09600	$1*(2-(-3+45))*(-67-(-8+9A+B))$	$B-A98-(-7-6543+2-1)$
5681	09601	$12+3-4-(-5678+9+A-B)$	$BA+98-(-76-5432+1)$
5682	09602	$1-(2-3)-(4-5678)-(-9-A+B)$	$BA9-87^*-65-4-32^*1$
5683	09603	$12-3+4+5678-9-A+B$	$-B-A^*-98+765+4321$
5684	09604	$12*(3-4)*(5-6-(-7+89))-A+B$	$-B-(A98-7)+6543+21$
5685	09605	$1+23-45-6*(7+8)*(-9A+B)$	$-BA+9*(8+765)+43-(-2-1)$
5686	09606	$1+2+3-4+5678+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*(765-4*(-3-21))$
5687	09607	$12-(-3-4)-(-5678+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8-7*(6-5^*4)^A3/2-1$
5688	09608	$1*23-4-(567-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$-B+A98+7*6^*54*3-2+1$
5689	09609	$-1+23-4+5678+9*(A+B)$	$-BA+987+654*3*(2+1)$
568A	09610	$-1+2-(3-4-5678+9-A-B)$	$BA9+87*65+(-4+32)^*-1$
568B	09611	$123-(-4-5-6)-7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$BA9-876-5^*4^*-321$
5690	09612	$-123+45^*-67+89A^*B$	$B-A98-7-(-6543-21)$
5691	09613	$-12-3-(-4-5678-9)-(-A-B)$	$BA9-8-7^*-65+4321$
5692	09614	$-12+3+4+5678-9-A+B$	$-B*(-A98-76+543+2-1)$
5693	09615	$-1-23+4+567-7*(8-9AB)$	$-BA-9*(8-(765+4))+3+21$
5694	09616	$-12-3^*-456*(7-(-8+9-A)-B)$	$B+A-9+(8*7+6^*5+4^*3)^A2^*1$
5695	09617	$12-(-3+4-5678-9)-(-A+B)$	$-BA9+87*(65-(4-32)-1)$
5696	09618	$1-2-(3+4)-(-5678-9+A+B)$	$B-A+9^*-8+(76+5)^*43^*2-1$
5697	09619	$12-(3-4)+5678+9-(-A+B)$	$-B-A9+87*65+4*321$
5698	09620	$12-(-34-5678+9-(-A-B))$	$BA9+87*65-(-4+3+21)$
5699	09621	$-1*(-2-3-4)*(567+89+A^*-B)$	$B-A^*9-(-87+6)*5^*4*(3+2)^*1$
569A	09622	$1-(-2+3+4)-(-5678-9-A-B)$	$BA9-8^*-7-65^*43^*-2-1$
569B	09623	$123-4+5678-(9+AB)$	$-BA-987+6543+21$
56A0	09624	$1-2+3-4+5678+9+A+B$	$B+A-9+8-7*(6-5^*4)^A3/2^*1$
56A1	09625	$12345-(-67+89AB)$	$B*(A9-(-8-76)-54^*3)^*21$
56A2	09626	$1234+5*(67+8+9AB)$	$B-A98+7-(-6543-21)$
56A3	09627	$-1+2-(-34-5678-(-9+A))-B$	$BA+9-8^*-7*6+5^*-4^*-321$
56A4	09628	$-1+23-4-(-5678-9+A-B)$	$B+A*9*8-(7+6)*(-543+21)$
56A5	09629	$1+2+(-3+4)*5678+9+A+B$	$BA9+8+7*65+4321$
56A6	09630	$-12-(-34-5678-9-A)-B$	$-B-A^*-9*8*7+6*543-21$
56A7	09631	$-1*(-23+4-(5678-9))-(-A+B)$	$-B+A9*8-7^*-6^*-5*(-4-32+1)$
56A8	09632	$-12+3+4+5678+9-A+B$	$B-(-A98-7*6^*54^*-3)+2-1$
56A9	09633	$1+2-3*(4-(56-78))*(-9A+B)$	$B+A*(-98-(-765+4))-(-3+21)$
56AA	09634	$-12+34-(-5678+9-A)+B$	$B+A+9+(8*7+6^*5+4^*3)^A2/1$
56AB	09635	$-1-(-23-4-5678)+9*(-A+B)$	$B+A+9+(8*7+6^*5+4^*3)^A2+1$
56AB0	09636	$-1+23-(-4-5678-9-(-A+B))$	$B*(A98+76-543+2-1)$
56B1	09637	$1*2-34-(-5678+9^*-A)-B$	$BA9+87*65-4+3*(2+1)$
56B2	09638	$12+3-45*(-67-89)-AB$	$-B-A*(98-765)-(4+32-1)$
56B3	09639	$-1+2*3^*4*(-5+67)-8^*-9AB$	$B+A+9-((-8+7*(6-5^*4)^A3)/2-1)$
56B4	09640	$1+23-(-4-5678+9-A)+B$	$BA9+87*65+4*(-3+2)^*1$
56B5	09641	$123-4+5678+9-AB$	$-B+A*9*8+7*(6-54)^*(3-21)$
56B6	09642	$123+4+5678-9A-B$	$BA9+8*(-7+65)+4321$
56B7	09643	$-1-2+3+4+5678+9-A+B$	$B+A+9+8-7*(6-5^*4)^A3/2+1$
56B8	09644	$-1-2+(-34-5678)*(9-A)+B$	$BA9+87*65-(-4+3)-(-2-1)$
56B9	09645	$1-(2-34-5678)-(-9A-B)$	$BA-9^*-876+(54+3)^*-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
56BA	09646	$1*(2+34+5+6)*-7*(89-AB)$	$BA9+87*65-4+3*2*1$
56BB	09647	$123+456*-7-89A*-B$	$B*(A+98*7+6*5-(4-3))*-21$
5700	09648	$-1+23-4+5678+9+A+B$	$BA9-87*-65+4-(-3+2)-1$
5701	09649	$-12-34-(-5678-9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-98*76+543-2+1)$
5702	09650	$-1*(2+3)*(-456-7-89A-B)$	$BA9-8*(-7-654)+321$
5703	09651	$1-(-2-(34+5678)+9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A+9*(8+7+6*5+4^(3+2)+1)$
5704	09652	$-12+34+5678+9+A+B$	$B+A-9*(-8-7*6*5+4)*(3+2)+1$
5705	09653	$((1+2)^3+4+5^6/(7+8))*9+A-B$	$BA9-87*-65+4-(-3+2*-1)$
5706	09654	$-1-2-34+5678+9*A+B$	$B-A+9*876+(54-3)*-21$
5707	09655	$-1-2*34-(-5678-9-AB)$	$-B-A+9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3/2*1$
5708	09656	$1-2-34+5678-9-A*-B$	$-BA*(-98+76-54-(3-21))$
5709	09657	$1-2*34+5678-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A-9*(8-765)-4*3-2-1$
570A	09658	$-12+3*4*5678+9A-B$	$-B+A*9*87+6-54+321$
570B	09659	$1*-2*3-(-4+5+6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8*(-7-6+5)*(-4*32-1)$
5710	09660	$12*(345+6-(-78-9A)-B)$	$-BA-9*(-8-765)+4-(32+1)$
5711	09661	$-1*(2+34-5678-9A+B)$	$B+A-9+(-8*-7-6^5)/-4*(3+2)-1$
5712	09662	$12+34+5678-9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7*(6+5)+4^4(3^2)+1$
5713	09663	$-1-2+34+5678+9A+B$	$B+A-9+(-8*-7-6^5)/(4/(-3-2))+1$
5714	09664	$123+4+5678-9A+B$	$-BA-98*(-76+5)-43-2-1$
5715	09665	$1*2-34+5678+9A-B$	$-BA+98*(76-5)+(43+2)*-1$
5716	09666	$1+2-34+5678+9A-B$	$-BA-98*(-76+5)-(43+2)-1$
5717	09667	$-1+2+34+5678+9-(-A-B)$	$B-A*98*-7-6+543*-2*-1$
5718	09668	$1-2*-34+5678-9*(-A+B)$	$BA9+87*65-4+3+21$
5719	09669	$1+2+34+5678+9+A+B$	$-B*(-A+9-(-8-(-76-543-21)))$
571A	09670	$123+4+5678-9*A-B$	$BA9+87-65*-43*2*-1$
571B	09671	$12-34+5678+9*A+B$	$BA9+87+65*-43*-2+1$
5720	09672	$1-234-(-56-7*(-8+9AB))$	$B+A-9-8*-7*((6+5-4)^3/2+1)$
5721	09673	$-1-23+4+5678+9*A+B$	$B-A+98*76-(543-2-1)$
5722	09674	$12*(3-45-6*-78+9*(A+B))$	$B+A+9-((-8-7-6^5/-4))*(-3-2)+1$
5723	09675	$-1-2-34+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6*5+4+3)^2-1$
5724	09676	$-12-3-4+5678-9A*-B$	$BA9+87*65+4+3+21$
5725	09677	$12-(34-(5678+9A-B))$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6*5+4+3)^2+1$
5726	09678	$12+3+(-4+5)*(-678-9)*-A+B$	$-BA-98*(-7-65)-(-43-21)$
5727	09679	$-1+2-(34-5678-(-9+AB))$	$-B+A*-98-765*(-4-(3+2+1))$
5728	09680	$-123-4+5-(-6+78*(-9A+B))$	$B*(A9+8-765-4*-321)$
5729	09681	$1-23+4+5678+9A-B$	$-B+A-(-9+87)*(-65-43+21)$
572A	09682	$-12-34-(-5678-9)+AB$	$-B-A+98*(7+65)-4-32+1$
572B	09683	$12345-6*7*(8+9)*(A+B)$	$-B+A+9*(8+765)-43*(2+1)$
5730	09684	$1-(2+34)-(-5678-9A)+B$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7)*-6+5)*-4*3+2+1$
5731	09685	$1-23-4+5678+9A*B$	$B+A+987*6-5-43*-21$
5732	09686	$-1-23-4+5678-9A+B$	$BA9-87*-65-(4+32)*-1$
5733	09687	$1*-23-4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+98*76-543-(2+1)$
5734	09688	$-12-(-3+4)+5678-(-9A+B)$	$B+A-(-98*76-(-543+2*-1))$
5735	09689	$1-2*(-3456+789-AB)$	$-BA+98*76+(-5+432)*-1$
5736	09690	$-123+4*-5*-6*78-9*AB$	$B+A987+6*-5*-4*-3*21$
5737	09691	$-1-23+4+5678+9-A*-B$	$-B-A-(-9-8+7*(-654-321))$
5738	09692	$123-(-4-5678)-9*A+B$	$B+A+98*76-543-2*-1$
5739	09693	$-1-2+3-(4-5678+9)-A*-B$	$BA+9*-8*-76-5*-432+1$
573A	09694	$1+2-3*4+5678+9A-B$	$-B-A-987-(-6543+21)$
573B	09695	$1-2-3-4+5678-(-9A+B)$	$-BA+9*(8+765-4+3+2-1)$
5740	09696	$1-23+4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A-9*(87*6*(-5+4)-321)$
5741	09697	$-1+2-34+5678+9A+B$	$BA9+87*65-(43+2)*-1$
5742	09698	$-1*(-2-(-34+5678))-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A*9*(-87+65)+4321$
5743	09699	$12-34+5678+9A+B$	$-BA-9*(-8-765)+4+3-2-1$
5744	09700	$-1+234-(56-7)-8*9*-AB$	$B+A+(-9+8-7+6^5/4)*(3+2)-1$
5745	09701	$-12+34+5678+9*A-B$	$B-A*98+765*(-4-3*2)*-1$
5746	09702	$12*(345-6-(-78-(-9+AB)))$	$B*(A+9-87+654+32*1)$
5747	09703	$-1-(-2-3+4-5678-9A)-B$	$B+A-9*8+(-7+6^5/-4)*(-3-2)-1$
5748	09704	$-1-23-(4-5678-9-AB)$	$B+A-9*8+(7+6^5/4)*(3+2)^1$
5749	09705	$1234+5-6*(7-89A-B)$	$-BA+987+6*54*(-3+21)$
574A	09706	$1-23-4+5678+9A+B$	$B+A+9-8+(-7+6^5/4)*(3+2)-1$
574B	09707	$-1-2+3+4+5678+9A-B$	$B+A+9-8-(7-6^5/4)^3(3+2)^1$
5750	09708	$-1-2-3-4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+9-8+(-7+6^5/4)*(3+2)+1$
5751	09709	$1*-2-3-4+5678-9A+B$	$-BA+9*(8+765)-(-4+3)^2*-1$
5752	09710	$12-34+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A+9*(-8+765)-4-3+21$
5753	09711	$-12+3+4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7-6^5/4)*(-3-2)/1$
5754	09712	$-1-23+4+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A*(-98+765)-4+32-1$
5755	09713	$1-(-2-(3+4))+5678+9A-B$	$B*(-A-98-(-765-(-43-21)))$
5756	09714	$1+234-(5-6*-7)+8*-9*-AB$	$-B+A-987+6543-21$
5757	09715	$-12-3-4+5678+9A+B$	$-B-(A-9*(-8+765))+4-(-32-1)$
5758	09716	$12+3-4+5678+9A-B$	$B-(A-(-987+6543)+21)$
5759	09717	$1*(-2-3+4+5*-6-78)*(-9*-A+B)$	$-B-A-987+6543+2*-1$
575A	09718	$1-2-(3-4-5678+9-AB)$	$-B-(A+987)+6543-(2-1)$
575B	09719	$-1+2-(3-(-4-(-5678-9A)+B))$	$-B-A-987-6543*(-2+1)$
5760	09720	$-1+2-3-(-4-5678)-9A+B$	$BA9-87*-65+43+21$
5761	09721	$-12+3-(4-(5678-(-9-AB)))$	$-BA9-87*(-65+4-32)+1$
5762	09722	$12-3-4+5678-(-9A*-B)$	$-B-A-987+6543+2+1$
5763	09723	$-12-(3-4-(5678+9A+B))$	$-B-A+9*(-8+765)-43*(-2+1)$
5764	09724	$1-(-234-5-6*-7-8*9*AB)$	$BA9-876+5432-1$
5765	09725	$-1+23-(4-5678-9A-B)$	$BA9-876+5432*1$
5766	09726	$-1-2-3-(4-5678-9-AB)$	$BA9-876+5432+1$
5767	09727	$12-3*4+5678+9A+B$	$-B-A-(9+8)-765*(-4-3-2)*1$
5768	09728	$1+2+3+4+5678-9A+B$	$B+A+(9+8)*(7*6+(5*4+3)^2*1)$
5769	09729	$-12+34+5678+9A-B$	$-BA-9*(-8-765-4+3)+21$
576A	09730	$-1+2-3-4+5678+9A+B$	$B-(-A9+8*7*6-5432*1)$
576B	09731	$1-2+3+4-(-5678-9A-B)$	$B-(-A9+8*7*6)-(-5432-1)$
5770	09732	$1+2-3-4+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A*(-98+765)+43-2*-1$
5771	09733	$123-4+5678-9A-B$	$-B-A9-(87*-6-5432)+1$
5772	09734	$-1-2345-67+89*AB$	$B+A+(-9+8)*7-6^5/-4*(3+2^1)$
5773	09735	$123+45+67+8*-9*-AB$	$B-A-98*(-7-65)-4*3-2*-1$
5774	09736	$1-2345-67+89*AB$	$B+A-(987-6543+21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5775	09737	$-1-2-34*5-(-67+8)*(9+AB)$	$-B-(-A+987-6543)-2*1$
5776	09738	$12+3-4+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A-987-(-6543+2)+1$
5777	09739	$12+3*4*567-(-8-9A-B)$	$-B-(-A+987-6543*(2-1))$
5778	09740	$1+234*5*6+(7-8)*-9+A*-B$	$B-A-987+6543-2+1$
5779	09741	$123+4-(-5678+9A+B)$	$-B+A-987+6543-2*-1$
577A	09742	$1-2+34+5678+9A-B$	$-B+A-(987-(6543+2+1))$
577B	09743	$-123+4+56-78*(-9A+B)$	$B-A-987-(-6543+2*-1)$
5780	09744	$-12+34-(-5678+9)+AB$	$-B-A-987+6543+21$
5781	09745	$1+2*3*-4*-567-8*9*AB$	$BA9+87*65-43*-2-1$
5782	09746	$12-(-3-(4+5678))-(-9A-B)$	$B*(A98+76+5*-4*32*1)$
5783	09747	$-1+23-4-(-5678-9A-B)$	$B-A-98*(7-65)-4-3*2*-1$
5784	09748	$-1+23+4-(-5678+9-AB)$	$-B+A-9+87*6-5*-4*321$
5785	09749	$12+3-4+5678-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A-9*-87+654*(3-21)$
5786	09750	$1+23+4+5678-9+AB$	$-BA+98*(76-5)+4+3+21$
5787	09751	$1+2-(3*-4-5678)-(-9-AB)$	$BA9+87*65+4*321$
5788	09752	$-123+4*-5+67*(8+9A)-B$	$B-A-987-654*-3*(2+1)$
5789	09753	$-1+2+3+45-6+7*(-8-9A)*-B$	$B+A-9*-8*(7/6+5+4*3^2+1)$
578A	09754	$-1*2+(3+(4-5+6)^7)/8-9+A-B$	$B-A-9-87*-6+5432*1$
578B	09755	$-1+234-5-6+7-8*9*-AB$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6^5/4)/(3+2)^{-1}$
5790	09756	$-1-2-3*4*-56+7*(89A+B)$	$-B-A+98*(7+65)-(-4-(32-1))$
5791	09757	$12+34+5678+9A-B$	$B+A-9*87*(-6-5)-4-321$
5792	09758	$-1+23-4-(-5678-9-AB)$	$B-A+98*(76-5)+43*-2-1$
5793	09759	$-12-3*4+5678+9*(A+B)$	$-B+A*-9+8*76+5*-4*-321$
5794	09760	$-1*-2*-34*(-5+6)*(-7-8-9A+B)$	$B+A-(987-6543+2)+1$
5795	09761	$123+4+5678-9+A-B$	$BA9+8*(765-4-3*21)$
5796	09762	$123-(-4-5678)-9*(-A+B)$	$B+A-987+6543+2-1$
5797	09763	$123+4+5678-9-A+B$	$-BA+9+(-876+5)*4*(-3+2-1)$
5798	09764	$1-2+34+5678+9A+B$	$-B-(-A+987)-(-6543-21)$
5799	09765	$-123+4+5-6+7*(-8+9AB)$	$BA98+76*-5*-4*3*-2+1$
579A	09766	$-1-(-2-34)-(-5678-9A)+B$	$B-A-987+6543+21$
579B	09767	$1*2+34+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A+98*(7+65)-4*(-3-(2+1))$
57A0	09768	$1+2-(-34-5678)-(-9A-B)$	$-B*(A9-8-765+43+21)$
57A1	09769	$1-2*-3*(-45+6*7)*(-8-9-AB)$	$-B+A-9*-87+654*(3-21)$
57A2	09770	$1+(2+3)*(4+5*6*(7*8+9))+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7)*(-6-(5+4^3))*2-1$
57A3	09771	$123-(4-5678)-(-9-(A-B))$	$B+A-(9+87*-65-4*321)$
57A4	09772	$-12+3-(45*67-89A*B)$	$B+A+(9+8*7)*6*(5+4+3+2)+1$
57A5	09773	$123-(4-5678)-(-9+A-B)$	$B+A-9*-8*(7+((-6*5+4)/3)^{2/1})$
57A6	09774	$123-4-(-5678+(-9A)*-B)$	$B+A*(-9-(-87-654))-321$
57A7	09775	$1-2-(-34-5678)-(-9-AB)$	$B-A+9*(-8-765-(-4-3))*(-2+1)$
57A8	09776	$-1*(-23+456-7+8*-9A*B)$	$B+A+(9+8-(7+(6+5)^4))/-3*2+1$
57A9	09777	$-1+2+34+5678+9+AB$	$-BA-98*-76-54-321$
57AA	09778	$-1-2-(3*45-(-67+8))*(-9-AB))$	$BA9+8*765-432-1$
57AB	09779	$1234-5-6*(-7-89A-B)$	$B*(A9-8-7+6+543+2*-1)$
57B0	09780	$1+23+456*(7+8)-9+AB$	$BA9-8*765-(432-1)$
57B1	09781	$-123+4+5+67*(8+9A)-B$	$-B-A+987*6+54*(-3+21)$
57B2	09782	$-1-23-4-(5*6-78*(9A-B))$	$B+A-9*(-8-765)-43-21$
57B3	09783	$123+4+5678-9A+B$	$B-A-9*(8-765-4)+3*21$
57B4	09784	$1+2*34+5678-(-9A+B)$	$BA98-7*(-6-54)*(3-21)$
57B5	09785	$1+234-(-5678+9+AB)$	$BA9+8*(765-43-21)$
57B6	09786	$-1-23*45-6+78*(-9+AB)$	$-BA9+87-65*-4*(32-1)$
57B7	09787	$-1+2-(-3-45*-67-89A*B)$	$-B-A*9+87*(-6-(-54+32*-1))$
57B8	09788	$(1+2)*3+4*(5+6*(7+8)^9))+A-B$	$BA9+8-7*-6*54*3-(-2-1)$
57B9	09789	$123+456*(7+8)+9-A-B$	$-B-A*9*-87-(-65+4-321)$
57BA	09790	$12+34+5678+9+AB$	$-B*A*(-98+76+5*-4*3-2-1)$
57BB	09791	$-12-(3-4-(-5-67+8))*(-9A-B))$	$B+A*-9*-87+6*(-5*-4*3+21)$
5800	09792	$123+45*(67+89)-AB$	$B+A+(9+8*7)*6*5+4*(3+2)+1$
5801	09793	$123-4-(-5678-9A-B)$	$-BA+987*6+543*2-1$
5802	09794	$-1+234+5678-9A-B$	$-BA-987*-6-543*-2*1$
5803	09795	$-1*(-234-5678+9A+B)$	$B-A-9-87*(-65+4+3-21)$
5804	09796	$1+234-(-5678+9A)-B$	$BA+9*8*7-6*(-54+3)*21$
5805	09797	$-1-2*(-3+45)+(-6-78)*(9*-A-B)$	$BA9+87*65-43*(-2-1)$
5806	09798	$-1*-2*-3*(-4*-56*7+89+AB)$	$-BA*(9-87-(6-5-43+21))$
5807	09799	$-12-3*-4*(567-(-8-9))+A*B$	$-B-A-98*-76-5-432-1$
5808	09800	$-1-2345-6-7+89*AB$	$-B-(A-9*(8+765+4-3))-21$
5809	09801	$-1*23*(45-(-6+78))*(9+A)*B$	$B*(-A+9)*(8+7-654-3+21)$
580A	09802	$1*234+5678+9-AB$	$B+A+(-9-8*(7+6-5^4+3))^2+1$
580B	09803	$1-(-234-5678-9-AB))$	$B+A+(9*(-8-7)*6+5)*4*3+2*1$
5810	09804	$-12+34-(56+78*(-9A+B))$	$-BA-9-8*-765+43*21$
5811	09805	$1*234+5678-9-A*B$	$BA98-7+6*-54*(3+21)$
5812	09806	$-12-345-67-8*-9A*B$	$B+A+9+8*7-6^5/4*(-3-2)^{-1}$
5813	09807	$-1+23-4+5678-9*(-A-B)$	$BA9+8*76+5+4321$
5814	09808	$12-3-(45-6)+78*(9A-B)$	$BA+98*76-543-2-1$
5815	09809	$-1+23+45*-67-89A*-B$	$B+A+9*(8+765)-(-43-2)*1$
5816	09810	$-1*(-23+45*67-89A*B)$	$BA9+8+7*6*54*3+21$
5817	09811	$1+23+45*-67-89A*-B$	$B+A-9+8*(7-6*5-4*3)^{-2-1}$
5818	09812	$-1-2345-(-6+7+89*-AB)$	$B*(-A-9+8*-7+654+32+1)$
5819	09813	$-12-34-56-7*(8-9AB)$	$B+A+9*8*(7+6-5+4^3*2)^{-1}$
581A	09814	$12*(-3+456+78-9A-B)$	$BA-98*-7*6-54*3*-21$
581B	09815	$1*-2345-6+7-89*-AB$	$-B-A-9-8*-765+43*21$
5820	09816	$-1-(-234-5678+9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8*(7+6+5))*-4^3+2+1$
5821	09817	$-1-(-2-(3+4^5+6)-7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA-9*(8-765)-(-4-3+21)$
5822	09818	$1+234-(-5678+9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9*-8-7+6)*(-5-4^3)*-2-1$
5823	09819	$1-2-(345+67)+8*9A*B$	$-B+A-98*-76-5-432-1$
5824	09820	$-12-34+5*6-78*(-9A+B)$	$-B-(-A-98*76)-(5-432*-1)$
5825	09821	$-123+45+6+7*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A+9+8*7*(654+321)$
5826	09822	$-123+4+5*-67-8*9A*-B$	$B-A-98*-76-(5+432*1)$
5827	09823	$1*234+5678+9-A*B$	$-BA-(9-8*76+5432*-1)$
5828	09824	$-12+345-67+8*-9*-AB$	$B+A*9*-87-65*-4*3*21$
5829	09825	$1*(2+3-4-(5-67))*(8-9)*-AB$	$B+A+(9-8-7^6)/(-5-4^3/2-1)$
582A	09826	$-1-2345-(-6-7+89*-AB)$	$-B-A-98*(-76+5)-4-3*(2+1)$
582B	09827	$1*-2345+6+7+89*AB$	$B+A+(9-8-7^6)/(-5-4-3)+2^1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5830	09828	$-1*2*-3*(-4+5)*(-6-7)*(-89-(A+B))$	$B+A+(9-8-7^6)/(-5-4-3)+2+1$
5831	09829	$12-34+5-(-6-78*(9A-B))$	$B-A9-87-6*(-54-3)*21$
5832	09830	$1+2-34-56+7*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A+98*76+5-432*1$
5833	09831	$-1-2+(-3-45-(678-9A))*-B$	$-B+A-98*-76+5-432+1$
5834	09832	$-1-2*(34+56)+7*(8+9AB)$	$BA+9-8-((76+5)*43*-2+1)$
5835	09833	$1+234+56*(7+8+9A+B)$	$-B-(A9+8*-76)-(-5432+1)$
5836	09834	$1+23*4+5678+9A+B$	$-B*(A-9)*(-8-76-543-21)$
5837	09835	$-1+2*(3-4)*(-5-6*-78*-9)+A*-B$	$BA+9*-8+765*(4+3+2)*1$
5838	09836	$-1-23+45*(67+89)-A*-B$	$BA-98*-76-543+21$
5839	09837	$-1+23*45*6-7+89A-B$	$B-A9+8*765-43*-21$
583A	09838	$12+3*4*567-(-89-AB)$	$BA+9-(8+7*(-654-321))$
583B	09839	$1/2*3*(4+5)-6*(7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+98-7*-65*(-4-3+21)$
5840	09840	$1*2+345-(67-8*9*AB)$	$-BA-9-87*(6-54-(32+1))$
5841	09841	$1-2-34+(56+7+8)*(-9+AB)$	$B+A-98*-76-5-(432+1)$
5842	09842	$-12-3-45-6*7*(-89-AB)$	$-BA-98*-76+5-(4+321)$
5843	09843	$-1+23*4+5678+9+AB$	$B+A+98*76-5-(432-1)$
5844	09844	$-1+23+4*-5-6-78*(-9A+B)$	$B-A98-7+65*4*(32-1)$
5845	09845	$-1*(-234-5678+9*A-B)$	$-B*(-A-98-(-7+6-(-543-(-2+1))))$
5846	09846	$-1*-2*(-3+456-78)*9*(-A+B)$	$B-(A-98+(-765+4)*3*(2+1))$
5847	09847	$12-3+4*5*-6+7+8*9AB$	$B+A+(9+8+7-6-5+4)^3*2*1$
5848	09848	$-12+3-45+6*7*(89+AB)$	$-B-A-(-9+8*-76)-5*-4*321$
5849	09849	$12+3*4+(-5-6+7*(-8-9A))*-B$	$B+A-98*(-76+5)-(-4+3)-21$
584A	09850	$123+4+5678-9*-A-B$	$-BA-9*(8-76)-5432*-1$
584B	09851	$(-1-(2^(3+4)+5/6+7))*-8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*(8-(-765-4))-(-3-2)*1$
5850	09852	$-12+3-4-56-7*(8-9AB)$	$B+A-9-8*(-7-6+5^4+3)*-2/1$
5851	09853	$-12-(-34+5*-67+8*9*-AB)$	$BA-9+(87+65)*(43+2+1)$
5852	09854	$-1+234*5*6-78-(-9A+B)$	$BA98+7*(6-543)*-2*-1$
5853	09855	$1-2-3-((-45+6)*(78+9A)+B)$	$B+A+98*(76-5)-43+21$
5854	09856	$-1*(2345-6*7-89*AB)$	$B*(A+98-(-7+6-543+2*1))$
5855	09857	$12+3+4*5*-6*(-78-(-9A+B))$	$BA-987-(-6543+21)$
5856	09858	$-1+234+5+(-678+9*A)*-B$	$B-A98+7+65*-4*(-32+1)$
5857	09859	$-1234+5*(678+9AB)$	$-B-A*(-987-6*-54+3+21)$
5858	09860	$-12+3+4-56+7*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A*98*7-65+4*321$
5859	09861	$-12+345-6*7+8*9*AB$	$-B-A+9+87*6+5432+1$
585A	09862	$1/2*(3^(4+5)+6*7-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7/6)*-5*-4^3/2+1$
585B	09863	$-123-45+(6-78+9)*-AB$	$B-A-9+87*6+5432-1$
5860	09864	$1-23-45-67*(-8-9A)-B$	$B-A-9*(-8-765)+4-3+21$
5861	09865	$(-1-2^(3+4))*(-5-6)*7+8+9+A-B$	$B-A-9+87*6+5432+1$
5862	09866	$-1*-2*(3456-7*(8+9A)-B)$	$B+A+(9+(8-7+6+5^4)^3)/2-1$
5863	09867	$-123+4-5-6+7*(8+9AB)$	$-B*(-A-9*(8+76)+5+4-(-3+2+1))$
5864	09868	$1+2*3-4*-5*6*78-9*AB$	$B+A+(9+(8-7+6+5^4)^3)/2+1$
5865	09869	$12-3*-45-6-7*(8+9A)*-B$	$B+A+9+(-8-7*(-6-5)*4^3)*2-1$
5866	09870	$-1*(-2-34-5)*6*-7*(89+A*-B)$	$B+A+9-(-8-7-6+5)*(432+1)$
5867	09871	$12-3*-4-5+6+78*(9A-B)$	$B+A+9+(-8-7*(-6-5)*4^3)*2+1$
5868	09872	$123+4+5678-9+A*AB$	$B+A-9+8*76-5*-4*321$
5869	09873	$123-4*-56*-7-89*A*-B$	$B+A-9*8*(-7/-6+(-5-4^3)*2)^1$
586A	09874	$-1+23+4+(-5+6)*-78*(-9A+B)$	$BA-9*-8+7*6*(5^43-21)$
586B	09875	$-12-(-3+45-6-7*(-8+9AB))$	$B+A-9+8-7*(-6-5)*4^3*2-1$
5870	09876	$-1/-2*(3^(4+5)+6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9*(8+765)+43*-2-1$
5871	09877	$1+(-2+3^4/(5-6))*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9*876-5+43*-21$
5872	09878	$1+2+345+6*-7-8*-9*AB$	$-B*(A9-87-654+3+2-1)$
5873	09879	$-1-2-34-56*7-8*9A*-B$	$BA-987+6543-(-2+1)$
5874	09880	$-1-2-3-45+6-7*(8-9AB)$	$BA-987+6543-2*1$
5875	09881	$1-2-34-56*7+8*9*AB$	$BA-987-(-6543+2-1)$
5876	09882	$-1-2-(-34+5-6)+78*(9A-B)$	$B+A*-98*-7-65-4*-321$
5877	09883	$1+234-5-6*7*(8-9A)*B$	$BA-987-(-6543-2)-1$
5878	09884	$-12-345-(-6+7-8*-9A*-B)$	$BA-987+6543-2*-1$
5879	09885	$123-4+5678-9+AB$	$BA-(987-6543-(-2+1))$
587A	09886	$-1+2+34-5+6-78*(-9A+B)$	$B-A-9*(-8-765)-(-43+2+1)$
587B	09887	$1-23*-4*-5+6*7-8*-9A*AB$	$BA+98*(7+65)-(-4-3-2)*1$
5880	09888	$1+2345-6*(7-8-9*-A*-B)$	$-BA9-87-65*4*32*-1$
5881	09889	$-1234+5*67+89*A*AB$	$-BA9-87+65*-4*-32+1$
5882	09890	$123-(-4-5678-9)-A*-B$	$B+A+(-9*8+7-6)*(5-(-4*3)^2)^1$
5883	09891	$12-(34-5)+6*-7*(-89-AB)$	$-BA+9-8*-7*(-65-43*2)*-1$
5884	09892	$123-(4-5678-9A-B)$	$B-A+9*(8+765+4+3-2+1)$
5885	09893	$123+4+5678-9+AB$	$B-A-(-98*(76-5)-4-3)+21$
5886	09894	$-1*(-234-5678+9-(-A-B))$	$B+A*-9*-87*(6-5)-(-432+1)$
5887	09895	$-12-34-5+6*7*(89+A+B)$	$BA+9-8*-7*(-6+5-(-4-3)*21)$
5888	09896	$-1*(-2-3-(456-789))*(-A-B)$	$B+A*9*8-(76-5432-1)$
5889	09897	$-1-2*(-34+567)-8*-9AB$	$-B+A-9*-876-5-43*21$
588A	09898	$-1-23+4-56*7-8*9A*-B$	$-B-A-(-98*76+54+321)$
588B	09899	$1-(-234-5*(-67-89+A))*-B$	$B+A9-87*-65-4*-321$
5890	09900	$123+4+5678+9A+B$	$-B*A*(-98-(-7-6+5)-(-4-3-21))$
5891	09901	$-1+2-345-6+7-8*-9A*AB$	$B+A+9+87*6+5432-1$
5892	09902	$-1-234+567+8*9*AB$	$-B+A*(98-7+654)-321$
5893	09903	$123-4+5678+9+AB$	$B+A+9*(8+(7-6*-5*-4/3)^2+1)$
5894	09904	$1-234+567-8*-9*AB$	$BA9+8*(765-4)-321$
5895	09905	$1-2+3*4-56*-7+8*-9*-AB$	$-BA-98*-76-(-54+321)$
5896	09906	$12-3*45+6-7*(-8-9AB)$	$-B*-A+(9*8+7)*(6+(-5+4^3)*2)^1$
5897	09907	$1-23*45-67-8*-9AB$	$BA-987+6543+21$
5898	09908	$12+3+(-456+789)*(-A+B)$	$B+A-9-8*(7+(-6+5^4+3)*-2*1)$
5899	09909	$-1-(-2+3)+45*(-6+78-9-A*-B)$	$BA+9*8-7*(-654-321)$
589A	09910	$-123+456+7+8*9*AB$	$B+A-9+(-8-7*-6*5)*(4+3)^2*1$
589B	09911	$123+4-(-5678-9-AB)$	$-BA+9*(8+765-4+3+21)$
58A0	09912	$12*(345-6-(7-89)+AB)$	$B+A*-9+87*(-6-(-54-32)+1)$
58A1	09913	$-1-(-234-5678)-(-9-A+B)$	$-BA-(-9+8+(7+6-(-5-4))*-321)$
58A2	09914	$-1*(-234-5678+9-A+B)$	$BA+98*(76-5)-4*(-3+21)$
58A3	09915	$1-(-234-(5678-9))-(-A+B)$	$-B+A98*7-654-32*1$
58A4	09916	$-12-34+5+6*7*(8+9A)+B$	$-B-A+98*7*6-543*-2+1$
58A5	09917	$-1-(-2-345-6+7)+8*-9*-AB$	$-BA-98*-7-6+5432-1$
58A6	09918	$123*(45-6-(7-8)+9-A+B)$	$B-A*(98+7)-(-6543+2*1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
58A7	09919	$1+2+3+4-(-6+7)+8^*-9^*-AB$	$-BA-98^*-7-6-(-5432-1)$
58A8	09920	$1^*-2^*(-3456-7^*-89+AB)$	$BA-9^*-876+(-5-43)^*21$
58A9	09921	$-123+45-6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$BA+9^*(8-(-765+4))+3-21$
58AA	09922	$(-1+(-2-3))^*-4^*(-5/6+7^*8))^*9-(A-B)$	$-B^*(A+987-6-5^*(4+321))$
58AB	09923	$-1+2-3^*-4+5+6-78^*(-9A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7^*-6-5^*4)-3^*2/1$
58B0	09924	$-1+2^*(3+4)^*(-5+6^*7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*7^*-6^*(-5+4^*3)/2^*1$
58B1	09925	$-12-(34+56)+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B-A98^*-7-654-(3+21)$
58B2	09926	$12^*(34+567-8+9-AB)$	$-B+A9^*(-8+765+4-3+21)$
58B3	09927	$1^*(2-(-3-4))^*-5-(-6-(789-A))+B)$	$-B-A-9^*(-876-5)+43^*-21$
58B4	09928	$-12-3^*456+78^*(9A+B)$	$BA+9^*(8+765)+43^*(-2+1)$
58B5	09929	$-1+23-(4+5-6^*-7^*(-89-AB))$	$-B+A^*-9^*(-87-6)-5^*(-43+21)$
58B6	09930	$-1+2+(3-4+56)^*-7-8^*-9A^*B$	$B+A+9^*(-8^*7+(6^*5-4^*3)^*2+1)$
58B7	09931	$-1+234+5678+9A-B$	$-BA-98^*-7+6+5432+1$
58B8	09932	$-1+234+5678-9^*(A-B)$	$BA9+8^*765-4-321$
58B9	09933	$-1+234-(-5678-9)-(A-B)$	$B^*-A9^*(87-65+4-32+1)$
58BA	09934	$-12-3^*-4^*(-5-(-678-9)-AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6+(-5^*(4+3)))^*2^*1$
58BB	09935	$-1+234-(-5678+9)+A+B$	$B+A-9^*-8-7^*(-6-(5+43)^*21)$
5900	09936	$-1^*(-2-(-3-45))^*(-6-(7^*8-9+AB))$	$B+A98^*7-654-32-1$
5901	09937	$1+234+5678-(9-(A+B))$	$B-A-(987^*-6+543^*-2^*1)$
5902	09938	$1-234-5+67^*(8-(9-AB))$	$B+A98^*7-654-32+1$
5903	09939	$1-23+(4-5)^*-67^*(8+9A)+B$	$-B+A^*(-98+765+43-21)$
5904	09940	$-1-2+3-4-(-5-6+7^*(8-9AB))$	$BA^*(9-8+76+5-43+21)$
5905	09941	$1-23^*45^*-6-7^*-8+9A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6)^*(5^*4-(3+2))^*1$
5906	09942	$-1+2-3+5+6^*7-8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+9-8^*-7^*-6^*(-5+4^*3)/-2^*1$
5907	09943	$1-(234+5^*6^*7^*(89-AB))$	$-B-A+(9^*-8^*-7-6)^*5^*4+3+2-1$
5908	09944	$1^*2^*(3+4-567^*-8-9AB)$	$B^*(A-98+7+654+3^*21)$
5909	09945	$-12-34+56+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A9^*(-8+7+65)-4^*32^*-1$
590A	09946	$-1-(-23-4^*-5)-(-67-8)^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A+((-9-8)^*-7^*-6+5)^*(-4-3)^*2-1$
590B	09947	$1+2^*(3-4^*5^*(-6-7))-8^*-9^*AB$	$-BA+98^*76-(-5-4)^*(-32-1)$
5910	09948	$-12+34-5-6-7^*(8-9AB)$	$-B+A9^*(-8+7)^*-65-(-43+21)$
5911	09949	$-1-2345-67+89A^*B$	$BA+98+(-76-5)^*-43^*2+1$
5912	09950	$-1-2-(3+4+5+67^*(-8-9A)-B)$	$-B-A^*9^*-87+65-432^*-1$
5913	09951	$1-2345-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9-(-8^*-7+6)^*-5^*4^*3/2+1$
5914	09952	$123-4^*56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B-A98^*-7-(654+3-2)^*1$
5915	09953	$-1+234+5678+9A+B$	$BA9-87^*(6-(54-3+21))$
5916	09954	$1^*234+5678+9-(A-B)$	$B+A^*(9+87+654)-321$
5917	09955	$1+234+5678+9A+B$	$-B^*(A+9+8-7-654+3^*(2-1))$
5918	09956	$1+234^*(-56+78)+9AB$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(7+6+5^*4/(3+2))-1$
5919	09957	$1-2-3-4^*5^*(6-7^*8^*9)-(A-B)$	$B+A-9^*8^*(7-(-6-5)+43)^*-2^*1$
591A	09958	$1234-5-6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A^*-98-7+6543-21$
591B	09959	$-1-2+34-(-56^*-7-8^*9A^*B)$	$B+A-9+(8-(7^*6-5))^*/(-4-3)^*(-2-1)$
5920	09960	$-1^*2^*-3^*-4^*-5^*(6-7-(-89-(-A-B)))$	$B+A98^*(7-(6-5))+432-1$
5921	09961	$1+234^*5^*6-7+8+9-A^*B$	$B+A^*(-9-8)^*7-(-6543-2+1)$
5922	09962	$1-234^*5^*6-(-7+8+9)+AB$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*((-7-6)^*-5+4+3))^*2-1$
5923	09963	$1+(2-3+4)^*5^*(6^*7+8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A-98+76^*(-5-43)^*2^*-1$
5924	09964	$-12+3-4-56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B-A+98^*76+5^*-4-321$
5925	09965	$-1-2-3-4+5^*(6-78-9)^*(-A-B)$	$B-A-9-8^*-76-(-5432+1)$
5926	09966	$-1-(-2+345)-(-6+78+9)^*-A^*B$	$-B^*(-A9-8-7+6-543+2+1)$
5927	09967	$-123-4+5+(6-78)^*-9A-B$	$BA-98^*(-76+5)-(-4+32)-1$
5928	09968	$12^*(345+6-(-78-9A-B))$	$-BA9-8^*-7^*65+4321$
5929	09969	$-1-(2+3)-(-4+56+7^*(-8-9AB))$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7/-6^*-5+(-4^*3)^*2)/1$
592A	09970	$1-2^*-34^*(56+7^*8)+(-9-A)^*-B$	$BA-98^*(-76+5)-(-4+3+21)$
592B	09971	$-1-234^*5+6789+AB$	$B+A9^*(8-7+65)-43^*-2^*-1$
5930	09972	$1+23^*-4^*-5-(-6+7-8^*9^*AB)$	$-B+A9^*8^*7-654^*-3-21$
5931	09973	$1-234-5-(67+8^*-9A^*B)$	$B+A^*-9^*-87+65+432+1$
5932	09974	$-1-23^*-4-56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A98^*7-654-3+2^*1$
5933	09975	$1^*-2-3+45-(6+7^*(8-9AB))$	$-B-A98^*-7-654-(3-21)$
5934	09976	$12-(3-45+6^*-7^*(89+AB))$	$-BA9-8-7-65^*-4^*32^*1$
5935	09977	$-1-2^*34^*56+7+89AB$	$B^*(-A9-8-(-765+4+32)+1)$
5936	09978	$-1-23-45^*(-67-(-8+9A))-B$	$-BA-98^*-76-54^*(3+2^*1)$
5937	09979	$-1+2-3+5+6^*7-8^*-9A^*B$	$B+A^*98^*7+65^*4^*3^*-2^*-1$
5938	09980	$-12-34-5-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A^*-98^*-7+(654-3)^*2-1$
5939	09981	$1-23+45+67^*(89+AB)$	$BA-9^*(-8-(765-4))-32^*-1$
593A	09982	$-12-(-345-67+8^*-9^*AB)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7+6)^*5^*4+3-2^*1$
593B	09983	$12+3-4+5+67^*(8+9A)+B$	$B+A+(9^*-8^*-7-6)^*5^*4+3-(2-1)$
5940	09984	$1-2-3+4-5+(-6+7-8)^*-9AB$	$B+A^*-98-7+6543+2-1$
5941	09985	$-1-(-2-34-5)-(-6+7^*(8-9AB))$	$B-A+9-8^*-76-(-5432-1)$
5942	09986	$-1-2345-6^*7-89A^*B$	$BA9+8^*(765-43)+2-1$
5943	09987	$-1^*(2345-6^*-7+89A^*-B)$	$B-(-A+9-8^*76)-(-5432-1)$
5944	09988	$-1^*(-2-3-4+56-7^*(8+9AB))$	$-B^*(A9-87-654-3-2-1)$
5945	09989	$-1+2+3+4+5+67^*(8+9A)-B$	$-B+A9+87^*6+5432-1$
5946	09990	$-1^*23^*(45-6^*78-(-9A-B))$	$-BA9-(8-7+65^*-4^*32^*1)$
5947	09991	$-1+23+45-6^*7^*(89+AB)$	$-B-A98^*-7-654+32^*1$
5948	09992	$12-(-3+4)-56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-BA9+8-7+65^*-4^*32^*-1$
5949	09993	$-1^*(2-3)^*45-(-67+8)^*(9+AB)$	$B-A^*-98^*7-(654+3)^*-2^*1$
594A	09994	$12-3-(-4+56-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B+A+(9+8-7^*(6-5))^*4-3^*(2+1)$
594B	09995	$-12+3-45^*(-67+8-9A)-B$	$-BA9+876^*5^*(43-21)$
5950	09996	$-1+2-3-45+6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A+(9+8-7/6)^*(5^*4+3+2)^*1$
5951	09997	$12+3+45-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6)^*(5^*4-3/2)^*1$
5952	09998	$-1-2-345-(-6-78)^*(9A-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7+6-5^*4+3)^*2^*1$
5953	09999	$1^*(-2-3+4)^*(-567+8-9A)^*B$	$-B-(-A98-765-4321)$
5954	10000	$1^*2^*(3-(4-5))^*(67-8-9^*-AB)$	$-B+A^*-98+7+6543+21$
5955	10001	$-1+2+34-5-67^*(-8-9A)+B$	$B-A^*-9^*(8+76-(-5-(4+3-(-2+1))))$
5956	10002	$-1+234+5678+9^*A-B$	$B+A^*(98-7+654-32)+1$
5957	10003	$-1-23+(-4-5)^*-678+9AB$	$B-A98^*-7-654+3+21$
5958	10004	$1+234+5678+9^*A-B$	$B-A-98^*-76+(-5+4)^*321$
5959	10005	$1-23+4^*-5+6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$BA-9-87^*-6+5432^*1$
595A	10006	$-1-2^*(3^*-4^*(-5-6^*7+8))^*9A-B$	$-BA9+8+7+65^*-4^*32^*-1$
595B	10007	$-1+2-(-3-4-56+7^*(8-9AB))$	$-B+A9^*(876-5^*(43-21))$
5960	10008	$1-234^*-5+(-67+8)^*-9A-B$	$B+A-9+(8-7-6-5)^*4-3-2+1$
5961	10009	$1+2-3+4^*5+(-6+7-8)^*-9AB$	$-B-A^*(-98-(76+543+21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5962	10010	$12^*(34-56-(-78-9+A))*B$	$B^*-A^*(9-(87+6)+5+4)-3+2+1$
5963	10011	$12345+6-(-7-89)*-AB$	$BA+9-8^*-76+5^*4^*321$
5964	10012	$123-(4+5-6)+78^*(9A-B)$	$-B+A-98^*(-76+5)-43^*(-2-1)$
5965	10013	$1234-5+6^*7-8^*-9^*-A^*-B$	$B-A98^*-7-654+32^*1$
5966	10014	$-1+2-34^*-5^*6-7^*(-89A+B)$	$-B+A9+8^*(-765-4^*32)^*-1$
5967	10015	$12+3-(45-6)+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A+(9^*(8-7)+6-5)^4-3^*2^*1$
5968	10016	$1^*-2345-6-7-89A^*-B$	$-B+A9-(8+76)^*(-54-32+1)$
5969	10017	$1^*23^*-45^*(6+7-8-(-9+A+B))$	$B-(-A+9-8)-(7+6)^*(-543+2^*1)$
596A	10018	$-1^*(-2+34-(5+6)-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B+A-9+(8-7-6-5)^4+3+2+1$
596B	10019	$123+4-(-5-(67+8))^*(9A-B)$	$B+A-9+(8-7-6-5)^4+3^*2+1$
5970	10020	$1^*2^*(3456-7^*(89+A)-B)$	$BA+9^*(8+765)+4+32-1$
5971	10021	$1^*-2^*3-(-4^*5-6^*(7+8))^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A98+765+4321$
5972	10022	$1+2+34-56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B+A987+65^*-4^*(-3-21)$
5973	10023	$1^*2-3+(4^*5+6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B-A^*9^*-87-6-(-543+2)+1$
5974	10024	$-12-34^*-5-6-78^*(-9A+B)$	$BA+9-87^*-6-(-5432-1)$
5975	10025	$-12-3+45+(6-7+8)^*9AB$	$-B+A^*-9^*-87-6+543+2-1$
5976	10026	$1+234-(-5678+9-A^*B)$	$-B-A-(9-8^*(-7-6-5+43^*21))$
5977	10027	$-1-2345+6-7-89A^*-B$	$-B-A^*-987+65^*-43-21$
5978	10028	$1-2+34-5^*67-8^*-9A^*B$	$BA9+87^*(65+4)-(3+21)$
5979	10029	$12-3-(-45-67^*(8+9A))+B$	$-B+A^*(-98+765-4+32+1)$
597A	10030	$12-3+4-5^*6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A+9+(8-7-6-5)^4-3+2+1$
597B	10031	$1-2345-6+7+89A^*B$	$B+A+9+(8-7-6-5)^4+3-2^*1$
5980	10032	$-1^*(-2-3+45)^*(-67-8+9-AB)$	$-BA-9^*-87-(-6-5432+1)$
5981	10033	$1^*2^*3+(4^*5+6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8-7-6-5)^4+3^*(2-1)$
5982	10034	$1+2^*3-(-4^*5-6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A-98^*(-76+5)-43^*(-2-1)$
5983	10035	$-1/-2^*(3^*(4+5)-6^*-7^*8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A+98^*76-54^*3^*-2^*-1$
5984	10036	$1^*-2^*(34-56)^*(78-9-A^*-B)$	$-B+A+9-8-(7+6)^*(-543-2+1)$
5985	10037	$-1^*(2-34-56+7^*(8-9AB))$	$-B+A^*(-98+7)+6543-(2-1)$
5986	10038	$12^*(-345-(67-89A-B))$	$-B-A-(98^*7+6-5432+1)$
5987	10039	$-1-23+456-7+8^*9^*AB$	$-B+A^*9^*87+6+543+2+1$
5988	10040	$-12+3^*(-4+5)-(-6-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B+A+9+(8-7-6-5)^4+3^*2+1$
5989	10041	$-123+45-(-6+78)^*-9A+B$	$-BA-9-8+(7+6-5)^4+3^*21$
598A	10042	$-1+234-(-5678-9)-A^*-B$	$-B-(A-98^*7)-(-6^*543^*2+1)$
598B	10043	$-1^*(-234-5678-(9-A^*-B))$	$-B+A+98^*(7+65)-4^*3^*-21$
5990	10044	$1+234+5678-(-9-A^*B)$	$-B+A987+65^*4^*(-3-21)$
5991	10045	$-1+234-(-5678+9)+AB$	$-BA+98^*76+5^*-43+2^*1$
5992	10046	$12-3^*4^*(5+67-8)^*(9-A)^*B$	$-B+A9^*(-8+76)-54-321$
5993	10047	$1+234+5678-9+AB$	$-BA9+8^*-7^*(6+54)^*3^*(-2+1)$
5994	10048	$-1+2+3^*(-4-5^*-678-9AB)$	$B+A+(9+8-7^*(6-5))^4+3^*(2+1)$
5995	10049	$1+23^*4^*(5+67)+8^*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A^*-9^*-87-6-(-543-21)$
5996	10050	$1234-5+67+8^*9^*-A^*-B$	$B-A98^*-7-654+3^*21$
5997	10051	$-1-(2+(-3-4^*5-6^*(7+8))^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A-98^*-7+6+5432^*1$
5998	10052	$-1+234+5678-(-9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7+6)^*(-(5+4^*3)^*2+1)$
5999	10053	$12+34+56-7^*(8-9AB)$	$B-A^*-9^*-8^*(-7-6-5+4)-32^*1$
599A	10054	$1+234+5678+9A+B$	$-B+A^*9+8^*76+5432+1$
599B	10055	$1-23-(-456-7)+8^*9^*AB$	$B+A+(9^*8+7)^*((6-(5-4))^3+2)+1$
59A0	10056	$-12+3-(-456+7)-8^*9^*-AB$	$B+A+9^*((8+7+6^*5)/(4+3)+2)^1$
59A1	10057	$123-45-(-6-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B-A+98^*76-54^*3^*2^*1$
59A2	10058	$12-3^*-4^*(-5-(-6-78))^*9^*(-A+B)$	$BA9-87-6^*-54^*(-3+21)$
59A3	10059	$(1/-2+3)^*(4^*(5-(6-7))-8^*9)+A-B$	$-BA-(9-8)-(-7-6+5)^*-43^*-21$
59A4	10060	$1234+5+67-8^*9^*-A^*B$	$B+A^*-9^*-87+(-6-543-2)^*-1$
59A5	10061	$1234-5+6^*(-78+9AB)$	$B-(A-98^*7)-(-6-5432)^*1$
59A6	10062	$-1-23+(45+678)^*(9-A+B)$	$B+A98^*7+6^*-54-321$
59A7	10063	$-1+234-(-5678-9-AB)$	$-B-A^*(98-7)-(-6543-21)$
59A8	10064	$-123+4+567+8^*-9^*-AB$	$BA98-7^*6^*5^*(43-2+1)$
59A9	10065	$-1+234^*5+67^*89+AB$	$-B^*(A9-8-765-(-43+2^*1))$
59AA	10066	$1-(-23-4+5)-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B-A^*-9^*(-8-(7+6-5))^*(-4-3)-21$
59AB	10067	$12+3+4-5+6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-BA-9^*87-(-6543+2+1)$
59B0	10068	$1+2^*(3+4)^*(5+6^*7^*(8+9))-(A-B)$	$B+A+98^*76-(-54+321)$
59B1	10069	$-1-(-2-3-(-4^*5-6^*(7+8)))^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*-87-(-6543+2)+1$
59B2	10070	$1-2-34+56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A-9-8^*-7^*(65+43^*2+1)$
59B3	10071	$1234+5-6^*(78-9AB)$	$-B+A9^*8-76+5^*4^*321$
59B4	10072	$1+2^*(-3456-78^*-9A)+B$	$BA-98^*-76-5^*-43^*2^*-1$
59B5	10073	$1+2^*-34^*(5-6-7)+8^*-9^*-AB$	$-B+A9-8^*-765+43^*21$
59B6	10074	$-1-2^*3+456+7-8^*-9^*AB$	$-BA+9^*(8+765+4+32)+1$
59B7	10075	$1^*2+(3+4^*5+6^*(7+8))^*9+A+B$	$-BA+987^*6-5+4^*321$
59B8	10076	$-1+23-(-4+5)-(-6+7^*(-8-9AB))$	$-B^*(-A-9^*87-(-6-(5+4+3)))-(-2-1))$
59B9	10077	$1^*23-(-4+5)+6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B-A^*(9+8-765)+432^*-1$
59BA	10078	$-1+2^*3^*4^*5/6^*7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A9^*8+7-(-6543+21)$
59BB	10079	$-1+2-3+456+7-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B+A^*(9-8)^*(765-43-21)$
5A00	10080	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4+5^*67-(-89A-B))$	$B-(-A-98^*7+6-5432)-1$
5A01	10081	$-123-45-67+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B-A+9-8-76^*(-5-43)^*2-1$
5A02	10082	$1^*2^*(-3456-78^*-9A)+B$	$BA^*(-9-(-8-7)-(-6^*-5+4-32)+1)$
5A03	10083	$1-2+3+456+7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*5)^*(4+3^*2)^1$
5A04	10084	$12+3-(-456+7)-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7+6^*5)^*(4+3^*2)+1$
5A05	10085	$1+2^*-34-56^*7^*(8-(9+A)-B)$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7^*-6+5^*4+3^*2)^1$
5A06	10086	$-1+2^*3-(-456-7)-8^*9^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6^*5^*4/3^*(2-1))$
5A07	10087	$123-(-4567+89^*(-A-B))$	$B^*(-A-(-987+6)-(-5+4)-321)$
5A08	10088	$-1-23^*-4^*(5+6)+7^*89A+B$	$BA-9-8^*-765+43^*21$
5A09	10089	$1-2^*(-345+6)-(-78-9)^*A^*-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8^*-7^*-6^*5+4)^*-3^*2/1$
5A0A	10090	$-123-4-5-67^*(-8+9-AB)$	$-B-A+(9^*8+7)^*(6-5)^4+3^*2-1$
5A0B	10091	$(1+(-2+3-4)^5)^*6^*-7+8^*-9+A-B$	$-B+A9+8^*76+5432-1$
5A10	10092	$-1-2+3+45-6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B+A9-(-8^*76+5432^*-1)$
5A11	10093	$-1+23+456-7-8^*-9^*AB$	$BA9+8^*765+4^*3^*-21$
5A12	10094	$-12^*(3-(456+78)+9-(A-B))$	$BA9+87^*(65+4)-32^*-1$
5A13	10095	$-1+234+56-7^*(-8-9A)^*B$	$-BA-9^*87+6543+21$
5A14	10096	$-12+3-4+56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B+A+(9+8^*7)^*(6+5+(4^*3)^2+1)$
5A15	10097	$123+4+56^*-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$BA9-87^*-65-4+321$
5A16	10098	$12+34+5-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$B^*(-A+987-654+321)$
5A17	10099	$-1-2345-6-(-7-89A)^*B$	$-B-(A-98^*76-54^*(-3-2)^*1)$
5A18	10100	$-12+3^*-4^*(5-678)-9A^*B$	$B-A-9+(-87-6^*5)^*(-43-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5A19	10101	$-12+34+5^*6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B-A9^*8+7+6543-2^*1$
5A1A	10102	$-1+((-2-3^A4)^*5+6)^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A98^*7-6-(543+2)^*1$
5A1B	10103	$12-3+45-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A98^*7-6-(543-(-2+1))$
5A20	10104	$-1-234+5-67^*(8-9-AB)$	$-BA-98^*-76+54^*-3+2^*-1$
5A21	10105	$-1^*(-2-34-5)^*(-6+78+9A+B)$	$BA9+87^*65-(-4-321)$
5A22	10106	$1+23^*-45^*-6+7+8^*-9^*(-A-B)$	$BA+9-(-8^*765-43^*21)$
5A23	10107	$-1-2345+67+89A^*B$	$BA9+8-7^*(65-43^*21)$
5A24	10108	$12^*(345-(6-7-89-AB))$	$BA-9+8^*76+5432+1$
5A25	10109	$12+3+45-6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B-A^*(-98-(7-(-654+32+1)))$
5A26	10110	$1-2+3-4^*-56-78^*(-9A+B)$	$-B-A987+6^*54^*-3^*-21$
5A27	10111	$-1+2-3^*(-45-6)+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6^*5^*4^*3/2+1$
5A28	10112	$-1-(-2-3-4^*56+78^*(-9A+B))$	$B+A-9-8+7^*(-6^*(5+4/3))^2^A1$
5A29	10113	$1-2^*(3+456+7)-8^*-9AB$	$BA9+8^*(765+4-32-1)$
5A2A	10114	$-1-234-(-56+7)-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A9-8^*-76+5432^*1$
5A2B	10115	$-12-345+(67+8)^*(-9+AB)$	$B+A9-8^*-76-(-5432-1)$
5A30	10116	$(-1-(2+3^A4)+5-6)^*-7^*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$BA-98^*-76-5-(4+321)$
5A31	10117	$(-1+(2+3)^A4/-5^*(6-(7+8)))^*9-(-A-B)$	$B+A-9+(-8^*-7^*-6^*-5+4)^*3^*2+1$
5A32	10118	$1234-56^*(-78-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+(-6-(5+4/3))^2^A1)$
5A33	10119	$-1234-5+(-67-8)^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7)^*(6+5)^*43^*-2^*-1$
5A34	10120	$1+2^*(3+4+5^*6)+7^*(8+9AB)$	$BA+9^*-8+(-7-6)^*(-543-2)+1$
5A35	10121	$12+3+45+6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A+98-(-7-6)^*(543-2-1)$
5A36	10122	$-12^*(34-(-56-78^*-9)+A-B)$	$B+A+(-9/-8+7+6)^*((5+4)^A3-(2-1))$
5A37	10123	$-1+(2+3)^A4/-5^*(-6^*(7+8)+9)+A-B$	$B+A+((-9+8-7)^*(-6-5^A4)+3)^2^A1$
5A38	10124	$12-3-4^*56-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$BA-98^*-76-5+4-321$
5A39	10125	$-123-45+67^*(8-9)^*-AB$	$BA+9+8^*76+5432^*1$
5A3A	10126	$12-3+4+56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$BA+98^*76+5-(4+321)$
5A3B	10127	$((1+2+3)^A4-5^*6)^*(7-(-8-9))+A-B$	$B+A98^*7-(6+543-2+1)$
5A40	10128	$-1-234+56+7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A-9+8+7^*(-6^*(5+4/3))^A2/1$
5A41	10129	$-1-234-(-5-67+8^*9A^*-B)$	$-B+A^*987+65^*(-43+2-1)$
5A42	10130	$1-234-(-56-(7-8^*9A^*-B))$	$B-A^*-9+8-(-7-6)^*543-2^*1$
5A43	10131	$1-234-5+67-8^*-9A^*B$	$B^*(A+98-7+6+543+21)$
5A44	10132	$1-2^*(-3+456)-7-8^*-9AB$	$B-(A987-6^*-54^*3^*-21)$
5A45	10133	$-1234+56+(-789+A)^*-B$	$-B-A98-76^*-5^*(43-21)$
5A46	10134	$1-2^*-3456-78-9AB$	$-B+A^*(-9-8+765-43)-21$
5A47	10135	$1^*2-(-3^*(-4-5)^*6^*7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A9-(8+76)^*(-54-32)-1$
5A48	10136	$-123-4-(-56+7)-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A+(9^*8+7+6^A5/4)^*(3+2)^A1$
5A49	10137	$1+2-(345^*-6-7^*8^*(9A+B))$	$B+A-9+(8+7-6^*5)^A4/(3+2/1)$
5A4A	10138	$1-2-3^*(4+(-5-6^*7)^*8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+8-7+(6+5+4)^A3^*(2+1)$
5A4B	10139	$1-2-3^*(-45+67)^*(-8+9-AB)$	$-B+A^*(98-7-(-654-3)-21)$
5A50	10140	$1+(2^*3+4^*5)^*6^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^A(-6+5+4)^*3+2+1$
5A51	10141	$1-234+5-(-67-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8+7^*-6+(5+4)^A3))^2^A1$
5A52	10142	$1^*23+4+56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B^*(A9+8-765+43-21)$
5A53	10143	$-123-(-4-5+67+8^*9A^*-B)$	$-B-A98+7-65^*-4^*32-1$
5A54	10144	$-123+4-56-7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B-A98+7-65^*4^*32^*-1$
5A55	10145	$123+4^*5-67^*(-89-A-B)$	$B+A+9/(8+7)^A(-6-5-4)/3-2+1$
5A56	10146	$1-2^*3-(-4^A5+(-6-7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B-A+9^*(876-54)-321$
5A57	10147	$-1+2+345+(-678-9)^*-A+B$	$-BA-9+8-7^*-6^*5^*(43-2)^*1$
5A58	10148	$(-1-2^A(3+4)^*5-6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A+9^*(8-765-43)-(-2-1))$
5A59	10149	$(-1-2^A3+4^A5)^*6^*(-7-8)/9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*8+(7+6^*5+4^A3)^A2-1$
5A5A	10150	$1-2+3+4+56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B-(A+98^*(-7-65-4)+32-1)$
5A5B	10151	$1+2^*-34-56^*(-7-8-9-AB)$	$B+A98^*7-6-(543-21)$
5A60	10152	$-1-(-2-34)+56+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-BA-9^*(8+7)^*-65+43^*-2+1$
5A61	10153	$-1-23^*(45-6)-(-7-8^*9AB)$	$-B^*(-A-98-7+6-543-21)$
5A62	10154	$-1+234+5^*67-8^*-9^*AB$	$-BA+9^*(8+765-43^*(-2+1))$
5A63	10155	$12+3-456-(7-89)^*-A^*-B$	$B-A98+76^*5^*(-43+21)$
5A64	10156	$1+234+5^*67+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A+9+(8+7+6^*-5)^A4/(3+2)+1$
5A65	10157	$12+34^*5-67^*(-8-9A)-B$	$BA+9+8+(7+6)^*543-21$
5A66	10158	$1+2-(-34+5)-(-6-(-7+89))^*A^*B$	$-B+A-(-98+7+6^*(54+3)^*-21)$
5A67	10159	$-1234+567+8^*9AB$	$BA9-8+765+4321$
5A68	10160	$-1+2^*(-3-4)+(567+8+9A)^*B$	$-BA-98^*7-(-6543+21)$
5A69	10161	$1-2-3-45+(67+8-9)^*AB$	$B+A^*(987+65-4-321)$
5A6A	10162	$1-(-234+5)-(6+78^*(-9A+B))$	$-B-(A-98^*76)-(-5^*-43-2)^*-1$
5A6B	10163	$123-(-45-6)+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$-BA-(987+65^*-4^*-32^*-1)$
5A70	10164	$-1^*(-2-34)^*(5-6-(-7-(89+AB)))$	$B-A-9^*-87^*(6+5)+4+32^*-1$
5A71	10165	$12-(-34-56-7^*(8+9AB))$	$-B+A^*9^*87+65+4+3-21$
5A72	10166	$123-4+56-7^*(8-9AB)$	$-B-(A+9^*87)+6543-21$
5A73	10167	$-1+2^*3-45^*6-78^*(-9A+B)$	$B+A+9+8-7^*((6-(5+4)^A3)^2-1)$
5A74	10168	$1^*-234^*(56+7-89-A+B)$	$B+A-9-8-7^*(6-(5+4)^A3^2)^A1$
5A75	10169	$-123-4-(-5-67^*(8-9)^*-AB)$	$-B-A^*(9-8^*76)+5^*-432^*-1$
5A76	10170	$1^*(2+3)^*(4+5)^*(-6+78-(-9-AB))$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5+4)^A3^*(2+1)$
5A77	10171	$-1+234-(-5-67-8)^*(9A-B)$	$-BA9-(-87-65^*-43^*(-2-1))$
5A78	10172	$-1-(-2-3-4-5+(6-78)^*9A-B)$	$B+A+(9^*8+7^*6^*5)^*4^*3^A2-1$
5A79	10173	$-123+4+56+7^*(-8-9A)^*-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*6^*(5+4-3)^A2^A1$
5A7A	10174	$123+4+56+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A+9^*87-6-5432^*-1$
5A7B	10175	$-1-(23+456-78^*9A+B)$	$BA9+8+765+4321$
5A80	10176	$-1^*2^*(34+56)^*(78-(9+AB))$	$B-A+98^*76+5^*(-43-2)^*1$
5A81	10177	$1-23-456-78^*-9A-B$	$B+A-9+8+7^*(-6+(5+4)^A3^2-1)$
5A82	10178	$(1-2)^A3+(-4^A5+6)^*(7-8-9)+A-B$	$-BA+98^*76-5^*(-4+3+21)$
5A83	10179	$-1^*23^*(45-6^*78-9+AB)$	$B+A+(9^*8+7^*6^*5+4)^*3^*2^*1$
5A84	10180	$1^*-2^*(-3456-7^*-89-(A-B))$	$-B-A9^*(-87-6-5-4+32+1)$
5A85	10181	$1+2+(3+4^A5+(6+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A^*(-9+87+654-3-2)^*1$
5A86	10182	$1+23^*-45-(-6789-AB)$	$B+A-9+(8+7+(6+5+4)^A3)^*(2+1)$
5A87	10183	$-1^*(234+5+678^*(9-A)^*B)$	$-BA-98^*7+6543-2^*1$
5A88	10184	$1+2-(-345+6)+7^*(-8-9A)^*-B$	$-B-A9^*-8-76+5432-1$
5A89	10185	$-1-2^*(345-6-7-8+9-A)^*-B$	$-BA+98^*-7-6543^*(-2+1)$
5A8A	10186	$-12-(3+456)-(-78^*9A+B)$	$-B-A9^*-8-76+5432+1$
5A8B	10187	$-123-(-45+67)-8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA-98^*7+6543+2^*1$
5A90	10188	$-1-2-34+567-8^*9^*-AB$	$B-A-9^*87-(-6543+21)$
5A91	10189	$1^*-2-34+567-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B+A98^*7-(-65-(-432-1))$
5A92	10190	$1-2^*-3456+(7+8+9A)^*-B$	$-B-A+9^*-87+6543-2+1$
5A93	10191	$-1-2-3-(-4^*56-7^*(-8+9AB))$	$-BA-98^*-76-5-43^*2^*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5A94	10192	$-12 - (-3+456+78^*-9A+B)$	$-B - (A-9^*-87) - (-6543-2) - 1$
5A95	10193	$-12-3^*456 - (789-A)^*-B$	$-B-A-9^*87+6543+2^*1$
5A96	10194	$1-2^*3-4^*-5^*(6-7^*-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+7)/((-6^*-5/4)^3+2)^{\wedge}1$
5A97	10195	$1-234-5+(-678-(-9A))^*-B$	$-BA-98^*-76-54-32-1$
5A98	10196	$(1^*2+3+4^{\wedge}5+(6+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B-A+98+76^*(-5-43)^*-2-1$
5A99	10197	$-1^*(-2-34^*5+6-(-789-A))^*-B$	$-B^*(A-9)^*-87^*(-6+5)^*(4^*-3-(-2-1))$
5A9A	10198	$1/(2-3)+4^*5^*(6+7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$BA+98^*76-54^*-3^*-2^*1$
5A9B	10199	$1-2-(3+456-78^*9A)-B$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6)^*((5+4)^3-2^{\wedge}1)$
5AA0	10200	$1^*2^*(34+5+6)^*(78+9+A-B)$	$BA-98^*-7-6^*(543^*-2+1)$
5AA1	10201	$123-4-5-6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$BA-98^*-7-(6-5432+1)$
5AA2	10202	$-123-4+(5-6)^*7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$BA9+8^*(765-4^*3^*2)+1$
5AA3	10203	$-1-2-(-3+456)+78^*9A-B$	$BA-9^*-87-6-5^*-4^*321$
5AA4	10204	$1+23^*-4-56-7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
5AA5	10205	$1-2-(-3+456+78^*-9A+B)$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
5AA6	10206	$-12^*(-3-456-(78-9-A+B))$	$-BA-98^*-76-54-3-21$
5AA7	10207	$-1-23+4+567-8^*9^*-AB$	$-BA+98^*76+(5-43)^*2+1$
5AA8	10208	$-12-3-456-78^*-9A+B$	$B^*(A9+87)^*(-6-5+4+3)^*(-2+1)$
5AA9	10209	$((-1+2)^*-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	$-BA-9-8^*7^*(6-5+4)^*(-32+1)$
5AAA	10210	$1+23-4+(5+6)^*(7-8^*-9A-B)$	$B-A+9^*-87+6543-2-1$
5AAB	10211	$1+2^*3456-7-8-9AB$	$-B-A-98+(7-6)^*(-543-21)$
5AB0	10212	$1+2+(-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A98^*7+(65+432)^*-1$
5AB1	10213	$(1+(2-3+4)^{\wedge}5+6)^*7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A^*(9-87)+6543+2+1$
5AB2	10214	$12+3+4^*56+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$B-(A+9^*87-6543-2+1)$
5AB3	10215	$1234-5-67^*-89-AB$	$BA+98^*7+6+5432+1$
5AB4	10216	$-1-2+3^*-4+567-8^*9^*-AB$	$BA9+87-6^*(-5-43)^*21$
5AB5	10217	$1-2+3^*(4-5)^*(-6+7+89)^*-AB$	$BA9+8^*7+6^*-54^*(3-21)$
5AB6	10218	$1^*(-2+34+5+6^*-78-9)^*-AB$	$B+A-98^*(-7-65)-(4-321)$
5AB7	10219	$1-(2-3+45)-67^*(-8+9-AB)$	$B^*(A+9-(8+7)+654+3^*(-2+1))$
5AB8	10220	$12-(-3+456+78^*-9A)-B$	$-BA+9^*-87^*-6-54^*-3^*21$
5AB9	10221	$1-2-3-456+78^*9A+B$	$B+A+9^*-87^*(-6+5^*(-4+3))+21$
5ABA	10222	$(1+2^*3-4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
5ABB	10223	$-1-23-(45^*-6-7^*(-8+9AB))$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
5B00	10224	$-1-234^*-56-(7-8^*-9AB)$	$-BA^*9^*(-87+65-4-3+21)$
5B01	10225	$1234+5678-9AB$	$-B-A-(9-87)^*(65-(-4-3-21))$
5B02	10226	$1-23-45-67-8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A^*(9-87-654)-(-3-2)^*-1$
5B03	10227	$-1^*-2^*((-3+4^{\wedge}5)^*(6+7-8)+9)+A-B$	$-BA+98^*76+5-43-21$
5B04	10228	$1+2+345^*6-7^*(89-A)^*-B$	$B+A9+8-76^*(5+43)^*2^*-1$
5B05	10229	$1-2+3-(4-(567-8^*-9^*AB))$	$B+A+9/8^*7^*6^{\wedge}(5-4+3)+2^*1$
5B06	10230	$-1^*(-2-3-4+5-6-78+9)^*-A^*-B$	$B^*(-A9+87-(-654-3-21))$
5B07	10231	$1+23-(456+78^*-9A)-B$	$B+A+9^*-87-(6543-2)^*-1$
5B08	10232	$-1+2-3+4+56^*(7+8-(-9-AB))$	$-BA+98^*76-54-3-(-2+1)$
5B09	10233	$-1+2-3+4-(-567-8^*-9^*-AB)$	$-BA+98^*76-(54+3+2^*-1)$
5B0A	10234	$1^*(2-(34+5))^*(-6-78-9-AB)$	$BA9-87+65^*4^*(3+21)$
5B0B	10235	$-12-3-(45+67+8^*-9A^*B)$	$BA9+87^*-6+5^*4^*321$
5B10	10236	$1234-(5+67^*-89+A^*B)$	$-B+A-9^*87+6543+21$
5B11	10237	$1-2-(-3-(4+567))+8^*-9^*-AB$	$-BA+98^*76+5^*-4^*3-(-2-1)$
5B12	10238	$1^*-2^*(345^*-6^*7+89AB)$	$-BA+98^*76-54+3+2-1$
5B13	10239	$-1+23^*45+(6+78)^*9^*A-B$	$-BA-98^*-76-5-43-2-1$
5B14	10240	$1-(23-45^*-6)-7^*-8^*9^*(A+B)$	$-BA+98^*76-(54-3)+2+1$
5B15	10241	$1-2^*-3456-(-7-8)-9AB$	$-B^*(-A+98-76+5+43-2-1)$
5B16	10242	$12-34^*5+67^*(-8+9+AB)$	$B+A987-6^*-54^*(3-21)$
5B17	10243	$-1+23-45-67^*(-8+9-AB)$	$B-A98+7+65^*43^*(2+1)$
5B18	10244	$12-34-5^*67^*(89-AB)$	$-BA-98^*-76-5-43+2^*1$
5B19	10245	$1+234^*5-678^*-9^*(-A+B)$	$-BA+98^*76-5-43+2+1$
5B1A	10246	$-12-34-5-67-8^*-9A^*B$	$BA9-8^*76-(-5432+1)$
5B1B	10247	$1+23-4+5+(-67-8+9)^*-AB$	$B-A9-(-8-7)^*(-65-432)^*-1$
5B20	10248	$12^*3^*-4^*(-56+7-(-8+9))-(-A+B))$	$BA9-8^*76-(-5432-1)$
5B21	10249	$-12-3-4+5^*-67^*(89-AB)$	$B-A+98^*76+54^*-3^*(2-1)$
5B22	10250	$1-2-34^*-5+6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-BA+98^*76-5-(4+32)-1$
5B23	10251	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^*-4)^*(5-6^*-7^*8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9^*8+7^*6^*(5+4)^3)/(2+1)$
5B24	10252	$123+456+7-8^*-9^*AB$	$-B^*(-A98+765-4-321)$
5B25	10253	$-1-(-23+4-567+8^*9^*-AB)$	$B+A-98^*-76+5-(43-2+1)$
5B26	10254	$1+2^*-345+(6+78)^*(9A+B)$	$-BA-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*-4^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5B27	10255	$-12+3-4-5^*-67^*(-89+AB)$	$B-A9^*-8-7^*6-5432^*-1$
5B28	10256	$-1-2^*(-34-56)+7^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A98^*7+(6-(-5-432))^*-1$
5B29	10257	$-1-234+5678-9^*A^*-B$	$BA9-87^*-65+432-1$
5B2A	10258	$1^*2^*(3456-78^*9+AB)$	$BA9-87^*-65+432^*1$
5B2B	10259	$-1+2-(34^*5-6^*(-78+9))^*(-A-B))$	$BA9-87^*-65+432+1$
5B30	10260	$-1-2-34^*5+67-8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA+98^*76-5+4-32+1$
5B31	10261	$-1+234-5-(-6-7^*(-8+9AB))$	$B-A+(98+76+54)^*32^*1$
5B32	10262	$12^*(-34+567-(-89+AB))$	$-B+A9^*8-7-6+5432^*1$
5B33	10263	$12-3-45-(-67-8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA+9^*876-(543+2)^*1$
5B34	10264	$-1+23^*(4+567)-8^*9AB$	$B-A9+876+5^*4^*321$
5B35	10265	$(-1-2/3)^*-4^{\wedge}5^*6+7+8+9-(A-B)$	$-BA+98^*(76+5)-(-432-1)$
5B36	10266	$-12-34^*(-56+7)+8^*9^*A^*B$	$-BA-9^*-876-543+2-1$
5B37	10267	$-123+45-(-6-7)+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-BA+9^*876-543+2^*1$
5B38	10268	$-1-(2+34-(-56-7))+8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA+9^*876-543+2+1$
5B39	10269	$1234-56+78^*-9^*-A-B$	$-BA-98^*-76+5^*-4+3^*(-2-1)$
5B3A	10270	$-1^*2^*(-3-(-4+56))^*(7+8^*9)^*(-A+B)$	$-BA+98^*76+(5-4)^*-3-21$
5B3B	10271	$1+2-3-45^*(-67-89-A)-B$	$-B+A9+87-6^*(-54-3)^*21$
5B40	10272	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6/7-8-9+A-B$	$-BA+98^*76+(54-32)^*-1$
5B41	10273	$1-2+3+4^*-5^*6+7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*7-6^{\wedge}5^*-4/3+2+1$
5B42	10274	$-1^*(-2+3+4^*5-678-9A)^*B$	$B^*(-A-9^*-87+6^*5+4^*3-21)$
5B43	10275	$-1-2+3^*(-456+7-8^*-9^*-A^*-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*(-7^*6^*-5+4)^3)^*2/1$
5B44	10276	$-12^*(-345-6-(7-(-89-AB)))$	$B+A+(9+8^*7^*(6+5^*4))^*(3^*2+1)$
5B45	10277	$12+34^*-5+6+7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-BA+9876-5^*-43^*-21$
5B46	10278	$-1-23-(-4+5)-(-6+7+8^*9A^*-B)$	$-BA9^*(-87-6-(-54-32-1))$
5B47	10279	$-1-23-4-56-7+8^*9A^*B$	$BA+9^*(8+76)+5432+1$
5B48	10280	$1234^*5^*(-6+7)-8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*(-87+6^*5^*(4+32)+1)$
5B49	10281	$1+2^*3^*(4+5^*6^*7)^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+98^*-7+6543-21$
5B4A	10282	$-1^*(2-3)^*45^*(6+7+8-(-9A+B))$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7^*(6+5^*4))^*-3^*2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
5B4B	10283	$-1+23+4^*5^*6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$-B-A-987+65^*-4^*-32-1$
5B50	10284	$(-1+2^*3)^*((-4^*(5-6))^{\wedge}7/8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A-(987+65^*4^*-32^*1)$
5B51	10285	$-1+2^*(-3-4)^*(5-6)^*-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B^*(A98-7-(6-5-(-432+1)))$
5B52	10286	$(-1-2/3)^*-4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2^*1$
5B53	10287	$-1+234-5-(67^*(-8-9A)-B)$	$B+A^*(-98-76)^*-5+4-3-21$
5B54	10288	$-1-234-567-8^*-9AB$	$-B-(-A-98^*76)+5+4^*(-32-1)$
5B55	10289	$-1^*(234-(-567-8^*-9AB))$	$-B+A9^*8+7+6+5432+1$
5B56	10290	$-12^*(-34-(-5-6^*(7+8))^*9)+A^*B)$	$-BA-9^*-876-543+21$
5B57	10291	$-123-(-4+5)+67-8^*9A^*-B$	$BA9+8^*765-43^*2^*1$
5B58	10292	$1+234-5^*-6-7^*(8-9AB)$	$-B+A-98^*-76+5-4^*-32^*-1$
5B59	10293	$-1-2-3^*(45-67)^*(-8+9+AB)$	$B-(A-98^*76)+5+43^*(-2-1)$
5B5A	10294	$-1^*(23-(-4-56+7))-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
5B5B	10295	$1-23^*4+5-(-6-7)+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-BA9+8^*(7-6+5^*4^*-3^*-21)$
5B60	10296	$-12+34-5^*-67^*(-89+AB)$	$B^*(A-(98-765+4+32)-1)$
5B61	10297	$-1+2-3^*(45+67)^*(89-AB)$	$-B+A-9^*(-8-765)+4+321$
5B62	10298	$-12-(3-4+56)-(7-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B+A9^*8+7-6+5432^*1$
5B63	10299	$1+2-3^*(-45-67)^*(-89+AB)$	$B-A9^*-8+7-6+5432+1$
5B64	10300	$1-234^*(-5+67-89)+AB$	$B-A98^*-7+6-(-5+432)^*1$
5B65	10301	$-123+4+5+6+7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+9^*(8+7^*6^*(5+4)^*3)+2^*1$
5B66	10302	$-12-34^*5-678^*(-9+A)^*-B$	$B-(A-98^*76)-(54-3^*-21)$
5B67	10303	$-12+3+4+5-67-8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A+98^*-7+6543-21$
5B68	10304	$12^*(-3+456-7-(-89-A)-B)$	$-B+A-987+65^*-4^*32^*-1$
5B69	10305	$-1+2+3^*-45+67-8^*-9A^*B$	$-B+A-987+65^*4^*32+1$
5B6A	10306	$1^*2-34-5+67^*(-8+9)^*AB$	$BA+98+(-7-6)^*-543+21$
5B6B	10307	$12-3-4-5-67+8^*9A^*B$	$B-A-987-65^*4^*-32+1$
5B70	10308	$-123+4-5-(-67-(-8+9))^*AB$	$B-A-9^*(8-765)-432^*-1$
5B71	10309	$-1-2-3-(-4+56+7+8^*-9A^*B)$	$-B+A9^*(8+7+6-(-5-43-2-1))$
5B72	10310	$12-3^*(45+67)^*(89-AB)$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^*5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2/1$
5B73	10311	$12+3^*-4^*-567+8^*9^*A-B$	$-B-A98^*-7+6+54^*-3^*(2+1)$
5B74	10312	$-1+2+3+45-(67+8)^*-9A-B$	$BA9+8^*(765-(4+3))-21$
5B75	10313	$1+2+3+4+5^*-67^*(89-AB)$	$B-A9^*-8-76^*(-54-32-1)$
5B76	10314	$1234-(5+6-78^*9^*A+B)$	$BA9-8^*-765-4-3^*21$
5B77	10315	$-1^*(2+3+45+(6-7-8^*-9A)^*-B)$	$-B-A98-(76-54)^*-321$
5B78	10316	$-1+2^*3456+78-9AB$	$BA-98+7^*6^*-5^*(43-2)^*-1$
5B79	10317	$12-3-(4-5)-(67+8^*9A^*-B)$	$BA9+8^*765-(43+21)$
5B7A	10318	$12^*(-3+4)^*(56-7-8-9A)^*-B$	$B^*(A+987-654+321)$
5B7B	10319	$-1+2-3-4-5+6+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$-B-(-A+98^*-76+5^*4^*(3+2+1))$
5B80	10320	$-1-23^*(4-5^*67)-(89+AB)$	$-B-A^*(-98+7-654)-(32+1)$
5B81	10321	$-12+345+6+78^*(9A-B)$	$BA-9^*-87-6^*-543^*2^*1$
5B82	10322	$1-2+345-6+78^*(9A-B)$	$BA9-8^*-765+4+3^*-21$
5B83	10323	$1-2-(-3+4+56)-(-7-8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA-98^*-76+54-32-1$
5B84	10324	$1234+5-(6+78^*-9^*A+B)$	$-B+A+98^*-7+6543+2^*-1$
5B85	10325	$1-23-(-4-5+6^*7-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B-A+98^*-7-(-6543-(-2-1))$
5B86	10326	$-12+34-5-67+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A-987-65^*4^*32^*-1$
5B87	10327	$(-1^*(-2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*((-6-7)^{\wedge}8-9)+A-B$	$-BA+98^*76+5-4+3+21$
5B88	10328	$-123-(456-789^*A)+B$	$BA+987^*6+54^*(3+21)$
5B89	10329	$1^*(-2-34-(567+8-9^*A))^*-B$	$BA9-(-876-5-4321)$
5B8A	10330	$-1+23+4-5-67+8^*9A^*B$	$BA+9^*87+6-(-5432-1)$
5B8B	10331	$-1^*(2-3/-4-5^*6)^*-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A^*-987-6^*(5+432-1)$
5B90	10332	$1-2-3^*(4+56)^*-7^*8-9AB$	$-BA+98^*(76-5)+432^*1$
5B91	10333	$1-2+3-45^*(-6+7)-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*(3/2+1)$
5B92	10334	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^*6)^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-BA+98^*76+54-(3+21)$
5B93	10335	$12+3-45-6-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-BA-98^*-76+(5-4)^*32-1$
5B94	10336	$-12+34+5-67+8^*9A^*B$	$B-A98^*-7+(-65-4)^*(-3^*-2+1)$
5B95	10337	$12+345-6-78^*(-9A+B)$	$B-A98+(76-54)^*321$
5B96	10338	$-1-2/-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6-7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B-A+98^*76-54-32-1$
5B97	10339	$1^*(-23+4^*5)^*(6^*-7-(8+9AB))$	$-B-A^*(-98-76-5+4)^*(-3-2)^*-1$
5B98	10340	$-12-(345-(-6-78^*-9A))^*-B$	$-B^*A^*(-9+87)^*(6-5-4+3-(-2-1))$
5B99	10341	$123-4+5^*6^*-7-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A+9-8^*7+6^*5^*4/3-2+1$
5B9A	10342	$(1+(2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5)/(6+7))^*8-9+A-B$	$BA-98^*-76-5^*(43-2-1)$
5B9B	10343	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^*(-4-5)^*6)^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A+98^*-76-5)-43^*2+1$
5BA0	10344	$-1-2-(-3+45)+6+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$-BA-9+876-(-5432+1)$
5BA1	10345	$-123+45-(-67-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$-B+A98^*7+65-(-432-1)$
5BA2	10346	$12^*(-3-(45+67^*8-9AB))$	$-BA-9-(-876-5432-1)$
5BA3	10347	$-1+2-3^*45-(678+9-A)^*-B$	$B+A+(9+8^*(7^*6^*5+4))^*3^*2^*1$
5BA4	10348	$1^*-2^*(3+4+(-567+89A)^*-B)$	$B-A98^*-7-(6+5+4)^*(32-1)$
5BA5	10349	$1-2/-3^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6)+7-8^*9+A-B$	$BA9+87^*-6-5432^*-1$
5BA6	10350	$-1/(-2^{\wedge}3^*4+5)/6^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$BA9-87^*6+5432+1$
5BA7	10351	$1+2^*34+5^*67^*(-89+AB)$	$BA-9^*87+6543-2-1$
5BA8	10352	$12-34-5-(-6+7+8^*-9A^*B)$	$-B-(A+9-876-5^*-4^*-321)$
5BA9	10353	$1-2-345-6-78^*-9A-B$	$BA9-8^*-76^*(5+4-3)^*-2^*-1$
5BAA	10354	$1234+5678+9A^*-B$	$-B-A98^*-7-6-(-54+321)$
5BAB	10355	$-1+2-345-6+78^*9A-B$	$-B-A9-(-876-5432+1)$
5BB0	10356	$1234-(-5-67^*89^*(-A+B))$	$-B-A+98^*76+(54-3+2)^*-1$
5BB1	10357	$1+2-(345+6)-78^*9A-B$	$-B-A9-(-876-5432-1)$
5BB2	10358	$1-2^*(-3456+7)-89A-B$	$-BA-98^*-76+54-3-2+1$
5BB3	10359	$12-3-(-4-(-5-67^*(-8+9)^*-AB))$	$B+A+987^*6-5+4^*321$
5BB4	10360	$-1^*-2^*(3+4)^*5^*(-6+7)^*(8-(-9-AB))$	$BA9+8^*765+4-(32-1)$
5BB5	10361	$12+3+4+5+6+7^*(-8-9A)^*-B$	$-B-(A-98^*76+54)+3^*-2^*-1$
5BB6	10362	$1^*2^*(-3+4)^*(567-89A)^*-B$	$-BA-(-9-876-5432+1)$
5BB7	10363	$-1+2-3+4^*-5-6+7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA+9-(-876+5432^*-1)$
5BB8	10364	$-12+3-4-5+(6-7)^*8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA+9-(-876-5432-1)$
5BB9	10365	$1-2^*-3456-(7+89A+B)$	$-B-A9^*-8+76+5432^*1$
5BBA	10366	$-1-(-2-34)-(-56-7+8^*9A^*-B)$	$BA9-87^*(-65-4-3)+2-1$
5BBB	10367	$-1-(23-45)-(-6^*-7+8^*9A^*-B)$	$BA9-8^*-765-(43-21)$
6000	10368	$-1^*23^*4^*(-56+78-(-9+AB))$	$-B-A9+8^*765+4^*321$
6001	10369	$1-2-(3+45-6^*7)+8^*9A^*B$	$-BA+98^*76-(5-43-21)$
6002	10370	$1-23+4-5+6+7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B+A-98^*-76-54+3^*-2+1$
6003	10371	$1+((-2^*3)^{\wedge}4+(5-6)^{\wedge}7)^*8+9-(A-B)$	$B+A-98^*-76-5^*(-4-(-3-21))$
6004	10372	$-1^*-2/-3^*(-4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^*8))-9+A-B$	$-B+A-9+876-5^*4^*-321$
6005	10373	$1+234+5-6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-B^*(A-9)^*((-876+543)^*2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6006	10374	$-12-345-(-6+78^*-9A)+B$	$B-A-9+876-5^*4^*-321$
6007	10375	$1-2-345-6+78^*9A+B$	$B+A-98^*-76-54+3-21$
6008	10376	$12-34+5+6+7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B+A^*-9^*8-(7-6543+21)$
6009	10377	$-1-2^*-3456+7-89A-B$	$-B-A+98^*76-5-(4^*3+21)$
600A	10378	$-123-45^*6-(78^*-9A-B)$	$B-A+9876+5432^*1$
600B	10379	$12-(34-(-56+7))-8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A+9876-(-5432-1)$
6010	10380	$12-(345-(6+78^*9A-B))$	$B+A^*-9-87^*6^*-5+4321$
6011	10381	$1+2^*-345-(-6789+AB)$	$-B+A-9^*-876-543-21$
6012	10382	$1+2^*3456-78-9^*AB$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^*5^*4/3-2+1$
6013	10383	$-12+345+6^*7^*(89+AB)$	$B+A+(-987+654)^*(3-21)$
6014	10384	$1-23-45+67-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B^*(A-9-(-8-7))^*(-6-(5+43-(2+1)))$
6015	10385	$-1-2-345+6-78^*-9A+B$	$-B-A+9^*876-(543+2-1)$
6016	10386	$1+23+45-67+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^*5^*4/3+2+1$
6017	10387	$-1^*-2/-3^*(-4-5^*6+7^*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8)^7+6^*5^*4/3-2-1$
6018	10388	$-12-3-45-6^*(-78+9)^*(A+B)$	$BA-98^*-76-54^*3-2^*1$
6019	10389	$(-1-(2^*3+4^*5+6))^*(7-8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A^*98-7-6+5432-1$
601A	10390	$1+2+3+4+5^*-6-7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-BA-98^*-76+54+3+21$
601B	10391	$-12+3+45+6^*7^*(8-9)^*-AB$	$BA9-8^*-765+4-3-2-1$
6020	10392	$-12+3-4^*-5-(-6+7)-8^*9A^*-B$	$BA9+8^*765-(-4+3-2^*-1)$
6021	10393	$-12-(3+45)-(-67-8^*9A^*B)$	$B+A98^*7-6^*(5^*-4^*-3+21)$
6022	10394	$1-2-3-4+5+6+7-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A-9+876-5^*4^*-321$
6023	10395	$1^*(2+3)^*(4^*5+6^*7^*8+9AB)$	$-B+A^*-9+876+5432^*1$
6024	10396	$123-456+78^*9A+B$	$-B+A+98^*76-(-5+43)-(-2-1)$
6025	10397	$-1-23+4-5-6^*-7-8^*-9A^*B$	$B+A+9+8-7+6^*5^*4/3-2^*1$
6026	10398	$1-23+45-6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$-B-A+9876+5^*-43^*21$
6027	10399	$-12-(-3+45-67)+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+9-8+7+6^*5^*4/3+2^*1$
6028	10400	$-1^*-2^*-34^*5^*(-6+7)^*(89-AB)$	$B-A+987+6^*5^*4^*-3^*-21$
6029	10401	$12+3+4-(5+6)-(-7-8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA+98^*76+54+3+21$
602A	10402	$12^*(-3+456+78-9A+AB)$	$B+A-(98^*-76+5+43)-(2+1)$
602B	10403	$-1+2+3^*-4^*-5+6^*-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-B-A^*-98+(-7+6)^*5432^*-1$
6030	10404	$-123+456+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$B+A-98^*-76-5-(43+2-1)$
6031	10405	$-12+3^*(-45+6)^*-7+8^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6+5)^4+3^*2+1$
6032	10406	$-1+2^*(3456+7)-(89A-B)$	$BA9+8^*765-4^*3+21$
6033	10407	$-1-2^*-3456-789-AB$	$-B+A+9^*876-543-(-2+1)$
6034	10408	$1-2^*(-3456-7)-89A+B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6+5)^4+3^*2+1$
6035	10409	$1+2^*3456-789-AB$	$-B-A98^*-7-6-5-4-321$
6036	10410	$1-23-(-45-(6-7))+8^*9A^*B$	$B-A-9^*-876-543-2^*-1$
6037	10411	$-123-(-4-5678)+9^*A^*B$	$B+A^*(9+87-654^*(3-2)^*-1)$
6038	10412	$-1-2^*3/(4-5^*6)^7(7-8)/9A-B$	$B-A-98^*-76-(5-4-(-3-21))$
6039	10413	$-1^*2^*3/(4-5^*6)^7(7-8)/9A-B$	$B-A+98^*76+(-5+4)^*(3+21)$
603A	10414	$-12+3+4+5+6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+9+8+7+6^*5^*4/3+2-1$
603B	10415	$-12+3+4-5^*(6-7)-8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A-98^*-76-54+32^*1$
6040	10416	$-12-(3+45-(6+78)^*(9A-B))$	$-BA+9^*876-5-(432+1)$
6041	10417	$1-(-2+34^*5)-(-67-8)^*(-9+AB)$	$-B^*(A-987-6-5-(4-321))$
6042	10418	$-12+3+4-5+6+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$-B+A+9876-5^*43^*21$
6043	10419	$12+3^*-4^*-5^*6+7^*(8+9AB)$	$BA9+8^*765+43-21$
6044	10420	$1+23-(-4-(5+6-7))-8^*-9A^*-B$	$B-A+9876-5^*43^*21$
6045	10421	$-12-3+45-(6-7-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B+A-98^*-76+5^*4^*(-3+2-1)$
6046	10422	$-1-234-567+89^*A^*B$	$B+A-98^*-76+(5-(4-32))^*-1$
6047	10423	$123-45-67-8^*9A^*-B$	$B-A-98^*-76-(-5^*4+32^*1)$
6048	10424	$1-234-567+89^*-A^*-B$	$B-(-A-98^*76)-(-5-(-4-3)+21)$
6049	10425	$1-234^*-56+78^*(9-AB)$	$B+A+9^*876-543-2-1$
604A	10426	$-12+3+4-(-5-67^*(-8+9+AB))$	$-BA+9^*876+5-432-1$
604B	10427	$-1-23-4+(-56+789)^*A-B$	$BA9+8^*765-4+32^*1$
6050	10428	$-1^*(234-(5-6+7+89A))^*B$	$-BA+9^*876+5-432+1$
6051	10429	$1-(2-34-5+6-7)+8^*-9A^*-B$	$BA-9-8^*(7+6-5^*-4)^*(-32-1)$
6052	10430	$12^*(-3-456+78-9A^*-B)$	$B+A-9^*-876-543+2^*1$
6053	10431	$-123-4-(5+(-6+7+8))^*9^*-AB$	$B+A+98^*76+5-(-4+32+1)$
6054	10432	$-1-2^*3^*(4+567)+89AB$	$B+A98^*7-(654-321)$
6055	10433	$-1-23+4+56+7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^*5^*4/3-2-1$
6056	10434	$12+3+4-5-6+7+8^*9A^*B$	$-B-A9^*(8-(76-5)-4)-3-2+1$
6057	10435	$1-(-2/-3^*(4-(5^*6+7+8))-9)-(A-B)$	$BA+98^*76+5+4^*32^*-1$
6058	10436	$-1-(-23+45-67+8^*-9A^*B)$	$BA9+8^*765+4-(-32-1)$
6059	10437	$123-4-5^*-67^*(-89+AB)$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^*5^*4/3+2-1$
605A	10438	$1-(23+4)-(-5-67)-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B-(A-98^*76+5)-(-4-3-21)$
605B	10439	$-12+3-(-45-6)+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$-B+A+98^*76+5+4+3^*(-2-1)$
6060	10440	$1+234+56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A+98^*76+5-43+21$
6061	10441	$1+2-3-4-5-(6+7^*-8)^*(-9-A)^*-B$	$-BA-98^*-76-5+4^*(32-1)$
6062	10442	$12-(34-5)+67-8^*9A^*-B$	$BA9-8^*-765+43-2^*1$
6063	10443	$1-2-(3-4)+56-7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B-A+98-(-7-6)^*(543+21)$
6064	10444	$-12^*(-34-567-8-9+AB)$	$-B-(A+98^*-76-54-(-32-1))$
6065	10445	$-12-(3-(4-5)-67-8^*-9A^*B))$	$-BA-98^*-76-5-4^*-32^*1$
6066	10446	$-1-234+5678-9^*-AB$	$BA-987+65^*4^*32-1$
6067	10447	$-1^*(234-5678-9^*AB)$	$BA-987-65^*4^*32^*-1$
6068	10448	$1-234-(-5678+9^*-AB)$	$BA-987+65^*4^*32+1$
6069	10449	$1-2+(-3+45)^*(67+8-9+AB)$	$B-A+98^*76-5^*4+3+21$
606A	10450	$1+2-3+45-(-6-7-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B^*(-A9-8+7-6^*5^*4^*-3^*(2+1))$
606B	10451	$-1-234^*(-5+6)-(-7+89)^*A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8^*7+6^*5^*4/3-2-1$
6070	10452	$-1+2-(-3-45+(6-7+8^*-9A^*)^*B)$	$B+A^*9^*(87-6+5+(-4-3)^*-2)+1$
6071	10453	$12+3+4+5+6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+9^*876-543+21$
6072	10454	$1-(-2-3+4^*-5)-67^*(8-9-AB)$	$B+A+98^*76+5^*(-4+3)-2^*1$
6073	10455	$-12-3^*-45^*-6+7+8^*9AB$	$BA+98^*(76-5)-4+321$
6074	10456	$12+3+4+5+6+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$-BA-9^*(-876+54)-(-3+2-1)$
6075	10457	$-1-2-3-(4-5)^*67-8^*9A^*-B$	$B-A+98^*76-(-5-4^*3+2)+1$
6076	10458	$12-3+4+5+6-7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-BA-(9-87^*(65+43-21))$
6077	10459	$12-345+6^*789A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(7-(6-5^*4^*3))^*-2^*1$
6078	10460	$1+2^*-345+6+7+8^*9AB$	$-BA+9^*(-876+54)^*(3-2)^*-1$
6079	10461	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+8^*9A^*B$	$B-(-A-9^*-8^*(-76-5-43+2-1))$
607A	10462	$-1+2-(3+4-5)-(-67-8^*9A^*B)$	$B+A-(98^*-76-5+4)-3-(-2-1)$
607B	10463	$-12-34^*-5-(67+8)^*-9A+B$	$B+A+(9+(-8+7)^*6)^*(5-4^*3)^2-1$
6080	10464	$-1-2+345^*-6-(-789A-B)$	$-B-A-(98^*-76-(-5+43-2)-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6081	10465	$(1+2+3-4)^5 * (-6^* - 7^* 8 - 9) - (A-B)$	$-B - (A+9) + 876 - (-5432+1)$
6082	10466	$-12 - (-3 - (-456 - 789^* - A - B))$	$BA - 98^* 7 + 6543 - 2 - 1$
6083	10467	$123 - 4 - (5+67+8^* 9A^* - B)$	$-B - A - 9 + 876 + 5432 + 1$
6084	10468	$-1 + 2 - 345^* 6 + 789A + B$	$B + A^* 98 - 7^* - 6 + 5432 + 1$
6085	10469	$-1 + ((2+3+4)^5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8) / 9 + A + B$	$B - A + 9 + 87^* 6^* 5 + 4321$
6086	10470	$1 + 2 + 345^* - 6 - (-789A - B)$	$BA + 98^* - 7 - (-6543 - 2 + 1)$
6087	10471	$-1 - (23 + 456 + 789^* - A - B)$	$BA9 + 8 + 7^* (6 - 5 - 43)^* - 21$
6088	10472	$1 - 2^* (-3456 - (7 - 8)) - 9^* AB$	$B + A + 98^* 76 + 5 + 4 - (-3 + 2 - 1)$
6089	10473	$1234 + 5678 - 9^* AB$	$-B + A - 98^* (-76 + 5) - 432^* - 1$
608A	10474	$-1 + 2^* 34 - 56 + (7 + 8^* 9A) * B$	$B - A98 + 7 - 65^* 4^* (-32 - 1)$
608B	10475	$1 - 2 - 3 - (-4 + 5) - (67 - 8 + 9)^* - AB$	$-B + A + 9^* (8 + 765 - (4 + 3^* - 21))$
6090	10476	$-1^* 2^* 3^* (4 + 5)^* (-67 - 8 - 9A + B)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 5 + 43^* - 2 + 1$
6091	10477	$1234 - 5 + 67^* 89 + AB$	$-B + A98 + 7^* (6 - 54)^* (3 - 21)$
6092	10478	$-12 - 34 + 5 - (678 - 9 + A)^* - B$	$B + A + 98^* 76 - (-5^* - 4 - 32 + 1)$
6093	10479	$-1^* (234 + 56 + (78 - 9)^* - AB)$	$-B - A + 98^* 76 + 54 - 3 - 2 + 1$
6094	10480	$-1^* (23 + 4 + 5 + 678^* (-9 + A)^* - B)$	$B - A - 98^* - 76 + 5 - (4 - 32)^* 1$
6095	10481	$-1 + 2 + 34^* (56 - (7 - 8^* 9 - AB))$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 54 - (32 - 1)$
6096	10482	$1 + 23 - 4 - 5 + 67 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$B + A - 98^* - 76 - 5 + 4 - 3 + 21$
6097	10483	$12 + 3^* - 45^* 6 + 7 - 8^* - 9AB$	$-B - A - (-9 - 876 - 5432) - 1$
6098	10484	$(1 + 2^{\wedge} 3)^* (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + (7 + 8)^* 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 98^* 76 + 5 - (4 + 3 - 21)$
6099	10485	$123 + 4 + 5 - 67 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$BA + 9^* (-8 - 7)^* - 65 - 43 - 2 + 1$
609A	10486	$12^* (3 + 4)^* (-5^* 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 + AB)$	$-B + A - (9 - 876 - 5432^* 1)$
609B	10487	$-1 + 2345 + 6^* 789 - AB$	$-B + A - 9 + 876 + 5432 + 1$
60A0	10488	$-12 + 3 - 456 - (789^* - A - B)$	$B - A - 9 + 876 + 5432^* 1$
60A1	10489	$1 + 2345 + 6^* 789 - AB$	$B + A - 98^* 76^* (-5 + 4) + 3 + 21$
60A2	10490	$-1 + 2 + 3 + 456 - 78^* (-9A + B)$	$-B - A - 98^* - 76 - 5 + 43 + 21$
60A3	10491	$1^* (-2^{\wedge} 3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6) / -7^* - 8^* 9 - (A + B)$	$-BA + 9^* - 8^* 7 + 6543 - 2^* 1$
60A4	10492	$-1 + 2 - 3 + 45^* - 6^* (-7 + 89 - AB)$	$-B + A^* 98 - (-76 - 5432) - 1$
60A5	10493	$-1 - 2 - 3 - 456 + 789^* A + B$	$-B + A98^* 7 - 6^* 54 - 3 - 2 + 1$
60A6	10494	$-12 - (-34 - 5 - 67 - 8^* 9A^* B)$	$-B - A98^* - 7 + 6 + 54 - 321$
60A7	10495	$1 - 2 - 3 - 456 + 789^* A + B$	$-BA + 9^* - 8^* 7 + 6543 - 2^* - 1$
60A8	10496	$1 + 2 - 3^* - 4 + (-56 + 789)^* A + B$	$BA + 98^* 76 - 54 + 3 - 21$
60A9	10497	$1 - (2 - 34 + 5 - 67 - 8^* - 9A^* - B)$	$-B + A + 98^* 76 + 54 - 3^* 2^* 1$
60AA	10498	$-1 + (2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4 / (-5^* - 6)^* (-7^* - 8^* 9) + A - B$	$B - A + 98^* 76 + 5 + 43 - (-2 + 1)$
60AB	10499	$-12 - 3 + 45 + 67 - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B + A98 - 7^* (6 - 54)^* (-3 + 21)$
60B0	10500	$12^* (-3 + 4 - (5 - 67^* 8 + 9 - AB))$	$-B + A9 + 876 + 5^* 4^* 321$
60B1	10501	$123 - (45 - 6) - 7 - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B - (-A - 98^* 76 - 5) - (4 - 32 - 1)$
60B2	10502	$-1 + 234 + (567 + 8 + 9A)^* B$	$-B + A - 98^* - 76 - (-5 + 43) - 2^* - 1$
60B3	10503	$-1 + 23 - 456 - (789^* - A + B)$	$-B - (-A - 9) + 876 + 5432 - 1$
60B4	10504	$1 + 234 + (-567 - (8 + 9A)^*)^* - B$	$-BA + 987 - 6 + 5432 - 1$
60B5	10505	$-1^* (234 - 5 + 67^* 8)^* (9 - A)^* B$	$B - A + 9 + 876 + 5432 - 1$
60B6	10506	$12 - 34 + 5 + (678 - 9 + A)^* B$	$-BA + 987 - 6 + 5432 + 1$
60B7	10507	$(1 + (2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5 - 6 - 7)^* (8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$B - (A - 9) - (-876 - 5432 - 1)$
60B8	10508	$-1 - 234 - (-5^* - 6 - 78^* 9A) + B$	$-BA^* (-98 + 7 - (-65 + 4 - 32^* - 1))$
60B9	10509	$-1 + 2^* - 345 - (-6789 - A + B)$	$-BA - (-987 - 6^* 543^* - 2^* - 1)$
60BA	10510	$1 - (2 + 3^* - 4^* 5^* - 67) + 89AB$	$-BA + 987 + 6^* - 543^* - 2 + 1$
60BB	10511	$12 + 34 + 56 - (-7 - 8^* 9A^* B)$	$-B - A - 98^* - 76 + 54 + 3 + 21$
6100	10512	$12 + 34 - 5 + 67 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-B - A + 987 - (6 - 5^* 4^* 321)$
6101	10513	$-1 + 234 + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8^* - 9A)^* - B$	$BA9 - 87^* (-65 - 4) + 321$
6102	10514	$-12 - 3^* - 4^* (5 - 67) - 8^* - 9AB$	$-B + A - 98^* - 76^* (5 - 4) + 3^* 21$
6103	10515	$1 - 2 / -3^* (-4 + 5^{\wedge} 6) + 7 + 8^* 9 + A + B$	$B - A98 + 76^* (54 + 3)^* - 2^* - 1$
6104	10516	$-1 - 2 - (-3 - 45 - (67 + 8^* - 9A^* - B))$	$-BA + 987 - (-6 - 5432 + 1)$
6105	10517	$1^* - 2 - (-3 - 45 - 67) + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-BA + 987 - (-6 - 5432^* 1)$
6106	10518	$1 - 2 + 3 + 45 + 67 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-BA - (-987 - 6) - (-5432 - 1)$
6107	10519	$1 - 234 + 56^* 7 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$B + A98^* 7 + 65 - 4 - 321$
6108	10520	$1 + 2^* 3456 + (7 + 8 - 9A)^* B$	$-B + A + 98^* 76 + 5 + 43 + 21$
6109	10521	$-1 - 23 - 45^* 6 - 78^* - 9A + B$	$BA98 + 7 + 6^* (-54 - 3)^* 21$
610A	10522	$-12 - 3 + 45 - (6 + 78)^* (-9A + B)$	$B - (-A9 - 876) + 5^* 4^* 321$
610B	10523	$12 - 34 + (5 + 6)^* 7^* (8 + 9A + B)$	$BA + 98^* 76 - 54 + (-3 - 2)^* - 1$
6110	10524	$-1 - 2^* 345 - (-67 - 8^* 9AB)$	$BA + 98^* 76 - 54 + 3 + 2 + 1$
6111	10525	$1 - (-2 + 3 - 4 - (5 - 678^* (9 - A)^* B))$	$B - (-A - 9 - 876 - 5432 + 1)$
6112	10526	$1 + 2^* - 345 + 67 + 8^* 9AB$	$B + A - (-9 - 876 + 5432^* - 1)$
6113	10527	$1 + 23 - (456 - 789^* A) + B$	$B^* (A9 - 8 + 76 + 543 - 21)$
6114	10528	$12^* (3 + 456 - (-7 + 8)^* - 9A - B)$	$B + A + (9^* 8 + 7)^* ((6 + 5^* 4^* 3)^* 2 + 1)$
6115	10529	$123 + 45 - 67 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-B - A9^* (8 - 76) - (-5 + 4 - (-32 - 1))$
6116	10530	$-1^* (23 - (-45 + 6 - 7)^*)^* (-8 + 9 - AB)$	$B - A^* 9 + 87^* (65 + 43 - 21)$
6117	10531	$-1 + 2345 - 6 + 7 + 8^* 9A - B$	$B + A - 9^* - 8^* (-7^* - 6^* 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) - 2^* 1$
6118	10532	$-12 - 34 + 5678 - 9^* A^* - B$	$-B - (-A - 987) - 6 - 5^* 4^* - 321$
6119	10533	$12 + 3 + 45 + 67 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$BA + 9 + 876 - 5^* 4^* - 321$
611A	10534	$123 - 45^* 6 + 7^* (8 + 9AB)$	$B + A - 9^* - 8^* (7 + 6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge} 3^* 2) + 1$
611B	10535	$(-1 - 2 / 3 - 4^* (5 + 6^* - 7)) * 8^* 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - 98^* - 7^* (6 + 5 + 4 - 3 - (-2 + 1))$
6120	10536	$(-1 - 2^* 3)^* 4^* (-5 - 6^* 7)^* 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9^* (-8 - 7)^* - 65 + (-4 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$
6121	10537	$-1 - (2^{\wedge} 3 - 4^* (-5 + 6^* 7)^* 8^* 9) - A^* B$	$-B - A + (-9^* (-8 - 7) + 6^* 5)^* 4^{\wedge} 3 - 2^* 1$
6122	10538	$-1 + 2^* 3456 - 789^* (-A + B)$	$B^* (-A - 9 - (-876 + 5^* (-43 - 2)^* - 1))$
6123	10539	$1 - (-2 - 345 - 6 - 7^* (8 + 9AB))$	$B + A + ((-9 - 8)^* - 7^* - 6^* - 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3)^* (2 + 1)$
6124	10540	$-1^* - 2^* (3 - 456^* (-7 + 8 - 9) + AB)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 54 - 3 + 21$
6125	10541	$((1 - 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5 / (6 - 7))^* (8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$BA + 987 - 6^* - 5^* 4^* - 3^* - 21$
6126	10542	$-12^* (345 + 6 - 789 - AB)$	$-B + A + 98^* 76 + 54 - (-32 - 1)$
6127	10543	$123 - 4 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-B - (A - 9^* (876 - 54)) - 32^* 1$
6128	10544	$-1 - 234^* (-5 + 6) + (78 - 9)^* AB$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - (5 - 4)^* 32^* 1$
6129	10545	$1 - (2 + 3 - 4^* (-5 - 6)^* (7 + 8 + 9)^* - A) - B$	$-B + A98 - 76^* 5^* - 4^* (-3 - 2)^* - 1$
612A	10546	$123 - 45 - 67^* (8 - 9 - AB)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 + 5 - 4 - 32 + 1$
612B	10547	$-1 - 2 + 34 + 5 - (-678 - 9 + A)^* B$	$B + A + 98^* 76 - (-54 + 3 - 21)$
6130	10548	$-1 - 2^* 34^* 56^* (-78 - 9^* - A) - B$	$B - A - 98^* - 76 - 5 - 4^* (-3 - 21)$
6131	10549	$1 - 23 + 456 + 7^* (-8 + 9AB)$	$-B - (A - 9^* 876) - (-5 - (-432 + 1))$
6132	10550	$12 + 345 - (-6 + 7^* (-8 - 9AB))$	$BA + 9^* 876 - 543 + 2 - 1$
6133	10551	$1 - 234 + 5 + 6 - 78^* - 9A + B$	$B + A + (98 + 76 + 54)^* (32 + 1)$
6134	10552	$(-1 + (-2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^* 6 - 7)^* 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 98^* (-7 - 6^* - 5)^* 4 - 3 + 21$
6135	10553	$-1 - 2 - (-345 + 67)^* (-89 + AB)$	$-B - (A9 - 8 + 7^* 6^* 5^* - 43 + 21)$
6136	10554	$1^* 2^* (3^{\wedge} 4^* 5^* (6 + 7) + 8) + 9 + A - B$	$-B + A^* (9 + 876 - 54^* 3) - 21$
6137	10555	$1 + 2345 - 6 - 7^* - 8^* 9A + B$	$B + A + (9^* 8^* 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5^* 4) / 3 - 2^{\wedge} 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6138	10556	$12^* (-34 - (-567 - 89 - A^* - B))$	$BA - 98^* - 76 + 5^* - 4 - 3^* 2^* 1$
6139	10557	$12 + 3^* 45 - (-6 + 7)^* - 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 54 + 32 + 1$
613A	10558	$-1 + 234 + 567 - 8^* - 9^* AB$	$B + A + (9^* 8^* 7 + 6^* 5^* 4 + 3) / (2 + 1)$
613B	10559	$1 + 2 - 3 - (-4^* - 567 + 89^* - AB)$	$B + A + 9^* (8 + 7 + (6^* 5 - 4^* 3)^2) - 1$
6140	10560	$1 + 234 - (-567 - 8^* - 9^* - AB)$	$B + A98 - 7 - 6^* - 5^* 4^* - 3^* - 21$
6141	10561	$1 - 2^* - 3456 - 789 + A + B$	$BA + 9876 + 5^* 43^* - 21$
6142	10562	$-1 - 23 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* - A^* B$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + 7)^* (-6^* 5 - 4^* (3 + 2)) + 1$
6143	10563	$-12 - 34 - 567 + 8^* 9AB$	$BA + 98^* 76 + 5 - (-4 - (-3 - 21))$
6144	10564	$1 + 2 + 3 + 45 - (-678 - (9 - A))^* B$	$-B - A987 + 6 - 54^* - 321$
6145	10565	$12345 + 6^* (7 + 89)^* (-A - B)$	$-BA - 987^* - 6 + 543^* (2 + 1)$
6146	10566	$((1^2 + 3)^4)^4 - 5 - 6^* 7^*)^* - 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8^* (7^* (6^* 5 + 4^* 3)^2 + 1)$
6147	10567	$1 - 234 + 5678 + 9A^* B$	$B - A^* 9^* - 87 + 6 + 5 - 43^* - 21$
6148	10568	$-1 / -2^* - 3^* - 4^* 5^* (6 + 7 / 8) + 9 + A - B$	$BA9 - 8^* - 765 + (4 + 3)^* 21$
6149	10569	$-12 - (-3 + 4) - (-5 + 6)^* 7^* - 8^* - 9^* (-A - B)$	$B + A - 9^* 8^* ((-7 - 6^* 5)^4 + 3 / 2)^{\wedge} 1$
614A	10570	$-12 + 34^* 5 - (-6 + 7)^* - 8^* 9A^* B$	$-BA + 9^* 876 - (5 + 4 + 321)$
614B	10571	$-1 + (-2^* - 3 + 4^* 5 + 6) / -7^* - 8^* 9 - (A + B)$	$B + A + (-9^* (-8 - 7) + 6^* 5)^4 + 3 + 2 / 1$
6150	10572	$-1^* - 2^* (-3^* (-456 - 789) - (-A - B))$	$-B - (A + 9^* - 8^* 76 + (5 + 4)^* - 321)$
6151	10573	$1^* 2^* (3 + 4^* (5 + 6)^* 7^*) (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + (8 + 7)^* (6 + 5)^* 4^* 3 + 2 - 1$
6152	10574	$-1 - (2 + 34 + 567) + 8^* 9AB$	$B - A987 - 6 + 54^* 321$
6153	10575	$-1 + 2 - 3^* 4 + 5678 - 9^* A^* - B$	$B - A - 9^* (-876 + 54) - 3 - 21$
6154	10576	$12 + 3 - 4^* 567 + 89^* AB$	$-BA9 - 8^* 7^* (65 - 4)^* - 3 + 21$
6155	10577	$1 + 23 - 45^* 6 - 78^* - 9A + B$	$-B - (A - 9^* (876 - 54) - (-3 - 2)) + 1$
6156	10578	$-1 + 2 - 34 - (567 - 8^* 9AB)$	$-BA - 9^* - 876 - 5 + 4 - 321$
6157	10579	$-12 + 3 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* A^* - B$	$-BA - 9^* - 876 + (5 - 4)^* - 321$
6158	10580	$1 + 2^* - 3^* (-456 - 789 - A) - B$	$BA - 9^* - 876 - 5^* - 4^* (-32 + 1)$
6159	10581	$-12 - 3 - (-4 + 5^* - 6^* 7) + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-B - (A9 - 8 + 7^* - 6^* - 5^* - 43 - (2 + 1))$
615A	10582	$1 + 2 + 3 - (4^* 5^* - 6^* - 7 + 8^* - 9AB)$	$BA - 98^* 76^* (5 - 4 - 3 + 2 - 1)$
615B	10583	$1 + 23^* (-4 + 56 - 7)^* 8 - 9A^* B$	$B + A + (9^* (8 + 7) + 6^* 5)^* 4^* 3 + 2^* 1$
6160	10584	$-123 + 4 - 567 - 89^* - A^* B$	$B + A + (-9^* (-8 - 7) + 6^* 5)^* 4^* 3 + 2 + 1$
6161	10585	$-1 + 23 + 4^* - 567 + 89^* AB$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 7^* 6^* 5^* 43^* (-2 + 1)$
6162	10586	$1^* 23 + 4^* - 567 + 89^* AB$	$B - A987 + 6 + 54^* 321$
6163	10587	$1 - 23 - 4 - (567 + 8^* - 9AB)$	$B + A + 9^* (8^* - 7^* (-6 - (5 - 4)))^* 3 - 2)^{\wedge} 1$
6164	10588	$1 - 2 - 3^* - 45^* - 6 - 7 - 89^* A^* - B$	$-B - (A + 9^* (-876 - 5)) + 432^* - 1$
6165	10589	$-1 - 2^* (-3 + 456) + 78^* (9A + B)$	$B + A + 9 + (-8 - 7)^* (-6 - 5) / 4^{\wedge} 3 - (2 - 1)$
6166	10590	$-1 - 2 + 3 + 4 + 5678 + 9^* - A^* - B$	$-BA - A^* (9 + 8 - 765) - (4 + 3^* 21)$
6167	10591	$12 - 34 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$BA + 9^* (8 - 7^* - 65 - 432^* - 1)$
6168	10592	$12 + 3 + 4 + 56 + 7^* (-8 + 9AB)$	$-B + A - 9 + (-876 + 54)^* - 3^* (2 + 1)$
6169	10593	$12 - 3 - 456 - 78^* (9 - AB)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 54 + 3^* 21$
616A	10594	$1^* - 23 + 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$B - A - 98 - 7^* 6^* - 5^* 43 - 2 + 1$
616B	10595	$1 - 23 + 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$-B + A98 - (76 + 5^* 4^* - 321)$
6170	10596	$-123 - (456 + 7 - 8^* 9AB)$	$-BA - 9^* - 876 + 5^* 4^* (3 - 21)$
6171	10597	$-1 - 2 + 3^* 5^* (67 + 89 - AB)$	$-B - A + 9 + (8 + 76 + 5)^* (43^* 2 + 1)$
6172	10598	$-1 + 2 - (34^* - 5 - 6 - 7) - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B - A^* - 9 + 876 + 5432 + 1$
6173	10599	$1 + 234 - 5^* - 67^* (-89 + AB)$	$B + A987^* - 6^* - 5 + 4321$
6174	10600	$123 - 4 + 5 - 67^* (8 - 9 - AB)$	$B + A - 9^* 8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4)^{\wedge} 3 + 2 + 1$
6175	10601	$-1 - 23^* 4 - 5^* 6^* 7^* (8^* - 9 - (-A - B))$	$BA9 + 8^* (765 - (-43 + 21))$
6176	10602	$-123^* (4 - (5 + 67 - 8) + 9 - (A - B))$	$B + A - 9^* - 8^* - 7^* (6 + (-5 - 4)^* 3) - 2 - 1$
6177	10603	$1^* 2^* 3^* 4^* 5^* (6 + 7) + 8^* 9 - (A - B)$	$B - A + 9^* 876 - 54^* 3^* (2 + 1)$
6178	10604	$-12 - 3 + 4 - (567 - 8^* 9AB)$	$-B^* (A9 - 8 - 765 + 4 - 3 - 2 + 1)$
6179	10605	$1^* - 234 + 56 - 78^* - 9A + B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7^* (6 + 5 + 4 + 3^* 2)^{\wedge} 1$
617A	10606	$-1 + 2 - 3^* 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7^* (6 + 5 + 4 + 3^* 2) + 1$
617B	10607	$12 + 3 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* A^* - B$	$B + A - 9^* - 8^* - 7^* (-6 - 5 + 4)^* 3 + 2^* 1$
6180	10608	$-123 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* - AB$	$B + A + (9^* 8 + 7)^* ((6 + 5)^* 4^* 3 + 2) + 1$
6181	10609	$-12 + 34 + 5 - 6 + 7^* - 8^* 9^* (-A - B)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 21$
6182	10610	$-12 + 3 + 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$BA - 98^* - 76 - 5 - 4 + 32 - 1$
6183	10611	$-1 + 2 + 34^* (-5 - 67) - 89A^* - B$	$-BA + 9 - 8 + 7^* (-6 + 543^* 2^* 1)$
6184	10612	$-1 - 23^* (-4 - 5 - 6^* - 7^* - 8) + 9A^* B$	$-B - A98^* - 7 - 65^* 4 - (-32 - 1)$
6185	10613	$1 + 2 - 3 - 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$-B + A9 + 876 - (-5432 + 1)$
6186	10614	$-12 - (345 + 6 - 789 + A + B)$	$B - (A + 987) + 65^* - 4^* (-32 - 1)$
6187	10615	$-123 - 45 - 6 + 78^* 9A - B$	$-B + A9 + 876 + 5432 + 1$
6188	10616	$-1 + 23 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* - A^* B$	$-B - A9^* - 87 + (6 + 54)^* - 32^* 1$
6189	10617	$1 - 2 - 3 - (-4 + 567 + 8^* - 9AB)$	$-B - A + 9^* (-8 - 76 + 5 - 43^* - 21)$
618A	10618	$1 + 23 + 4 + 5678 - 9^* - A^* B$	$BA + 98^* 76 + 54 - 3 - 21$
618B	10619	$-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$BA + 98^* 76 + (-5 + 4)^* (-32 + 1)$
6190	10620	$1 + 2345 - 6^* 789^* (A - B)$	$B - A - 98 + 7^* - 6^* 5^* - 43 + 21$
6191	10621	$1 + 2345 + 6^* 789 - A + B$	$B + A - 9 - 87^* (-65 - 43 + 21)$
6192	10622	$1 + 234^* - 5^* - 6 - 7^* (8 - 9A) + B$	$B + A - 9 + (8 - 7^* 6 - 5 - 4^* 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
6193	10623	$-1 - 2 - (-34 - 5678 - 9^* - A^* - B)$	$BA - 98^* - 76 + 5 - 4^* 3^* (-2 - 1)$
6194	10624	$123 - 4 + 56 + 7 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-B + A9^* (-8 + 76) - 5^* - 4 - (-32 + 1)$
6195	10625	$1 - (2 - 34) + 5678 - 9^* A^* - B$	$-B - A + 987 - 6 - (-5432 + 1)$
6196	10626	$12 + 3 + 4^* - 56 + (78 - 9)^* AB$	$-B^* (A - 9 - 8 + 7 + 654 + 32)^* - 1$
6197	10627	$-1 + 2 + 34 + 5678 + 9^* A^* B$	$-B - A + 987 - 6 + 5432 + 1$
6198	10628	$(-1 - 2)^{\wedge} 3 - 4^* (-5 + 6^* 7^*)^* - 8^* 9 + A - B$	$BA - (9 - 876 - 5432 + 1)$
6199	10629	$1 + 2 + 34 + 5678 + 9^* - A^* - B$	$B + A - 9^* (-876 - 5) + 432 - 1$
619A	10630	$1^* 2 - 345 - 6 - (789^* - A + B)$	$BA - 9 + 876 + 5432 + 1$
619B	10631	$1 + 23 - 4^* 56 - 78^* - 9A + B$	$BA9 - 8^* - 7^* - 6 + 5432^* 1$
61A0	10632	$123 + 4 + 56 + 7 - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B + A - 9^* (8^* (7^* - 6 + 5)^* 4 + 3 + 2 / 1)$
61A1	10633	$1 + 23 - (-4 + 5 - 6)^* (789 + 9)^* (A + B)$	$-B - A + 9^* (876 - 54 + 3) + 21$
61A2	10634	$1234 - 5 + 678^* 9 - A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6^* 5^* 4^* (3 + 21)$
61A3	10635	$123 - 4 + 5 + 67 - 8^* 9A^* - B$	$B + A9 + 876 + 5432 - 1$
61A4	10636	$1 + 2 - 3^* 4^* - 567 + (-89 + A)^* - B$	$B + A9 + 876 + 5432^* 1$
61A5	10637	$-123 - (45 + 6) - (-78^* 9A - B)$	$B + A9 + 876 - (-5432 - 1)$
61A6	10638	$12 + 3 + 4 - 567 + 8^* 9AB$	$-B - (A - 987 - 6) - 5432^* - 1$
61A7	10639	$1 + 234 + 5 - 67 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-B + A + 9 - 8 + (7 - 65)^* 4^* - 32 - 1$
61A8	10640	$1^* - 2^* - 34^* (-56 - (-78 - (9A - B)))$	$B + A - 98 - 7^* - 6^* 5^* 43 + 21$
61A9	10641	$-1 + 2^* - 345 - (-6789 - AB)$	$B + A^* 987 + 6^* - 5^* 4^* (3 + 21)$
61AA	10642	$1 - 2^* - 3^* 4 - 567 + 8^* 9AB$	$B + A + (9 + 8 + 7 + 6)^* 5^* 4^* 3^* 2 + 1$
61AB	10643	$12 + 3^* 4 - 567 - 8^* - 9AB$	$-BA9 - 87^* 6^* 5^* - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
61B0	10644	$1 - 23^* 4 - 567 + 89^* - A^* - B$	$B + A9^* (-8 + 76) - (-5 - (43 - 2)) + 1$
61B1	10645	$-1 - (2 + 3 - 4^* (-5 + 6^* 7^*)^* 8)^* 9 + A - B$	$-B - (-A - 987 + 6 - (5432 - 1))$
61B2	10646	$-1 - (2^{\wedge} 3 - 4^* (-5 + 6^* 7^*)^* 8)^* 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9 + 876 + 5432 - 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
61B3	10647	-1-2-345-6-(789*-A-B)	BA+9+876-5432*-1
61B4	10648	12+34-5*-6*7-8*-9A*B	-B*(-A-987+654-3)*2*1
61B5	10649	-123-(45-6+78*-9A)+B	B-A+987-6+5432+1
61B6	10650	1-23*-45+(678-9A)*B	-BA*(-9-8-7-(65-43+21))
61B7	10651	1-2-3+4*(5*6+7)*8*9+A-B	-B-(-A-987-6*-543*-2)+1
61B8	10652	-1+234-56+7-8*-9A*B	B+A+9*-8*(-76-54)-321
61B9	10653	1+2-(345+6)-789*-A+B	BA-98*-76-(5-43)+21
61BA	10654	-1-(2-34)-(567+8*-9AB)	B+A-9-8+(7+6+5+4)^3+2/1
61BB	10655	-123-45+6-(78-9)*-AB	-BA9+8*(765-(-4-321))
6200	10656	-1-234-(-5-(-6-78))*-9A+B	-B+A-98*-76-54*-3+21
6201	10657	123+456-78*(-9A+B)	-B+A-(-987-6-(5432-1))
6202	10658	1-2-(-34+5-6+78) *(9+A)*-B	-B+A+987*6-5*(4-321)
6203	10659	-1-2-345+6-789*-A+B	-B*(A-98-76-543-2)*1
6204	10660	1-(-2-34+567-8*9AB)	B-A+987+6-5432*-1
6205	10661	1-(23-456+7*(-8-9AB))	B-(A-987-6)-(-5432-1)
6206	10662	1234+5678+9*A*-B	B+A-9+(8+7+6+5+4)^3+2/1
6207	10663	-1+2-345-(-6-789*A)+B	-B-A-98-76*5*4*3*2*1
6208	10664	1*2-345+6+789*A+B	B-(-A+98)-(-7+6*54*(-3-21))
6209	10665	-1-2-34*-5*-6+78*(9A+B)	BA9+8*(-765+4-32) *1
620A	10666	-12+34-(5+67-8)*(-9-AB)	-B+A*(-9-8+765-4)+32-1
620B	10667	-1+2345+6*(789+A)-B	B+A+987-6-(-5432+1)
6210	10668	12*3*(45*(6+7-8)-(-9+A) *B)	B+A+987-(6+5432*-1)
6211	10669	-123-4+5-6-78*-9A-B	-B-(A9-8+76*5*4*3*2*1)
6212	10670	123-456-789*-A+B	-B*A*(-9-8+7-(65+4+3*2)) *1
6213	10671	12+34-567-8*-9AB	B+A+(9-8+7-6+5+4)^3+2*1
6214	10672	1-2*34-567+89*A*B	B+A+987-6*-543*2*-1
6215	10673	1+234-5-67*(-8+9) *-AB	B+A+9-8+(7+6+5+4)^3+2+1
6216	10674	1+2-(3+4)*5*-6-(-7+8*-9A) *B	B+A+9*-8*(7*-6+5)*4-3*(2-1)
6217	10675	-1-2*-3-(-45+67-8*-9A) *-B	BA+987-(6*5*4*-321)
6218	10676	-12+3+456-7*(-8-9AB)	BA+98*76-5*(-4-32-1)
6219	10677	123-4+5+(-678-9A)*-B	BA-98*-76+5*4-3*-21
621A	10678	123+4*-5+(-678+9A)*-B	B+A+9*876-54-321
621B	10679	-123+4-5+6-(78*-9A+B)	B-(-A-987-(6+5432))-1
6220	10680	1+2-3-4*(5-67)+8*-9A*-B	B-(-A-987-(6-5432*-1))
6221	10681	-1-2-(3-456)+7*(8+9AB)	B+A+987+6+5432+1
6222	10682	12*(3-(-4+5)-(67*-8-9A-B))	BA+98*76+5*4*(3*2-1)
6223	10683	1-2-(3-456)+7*(8+9AB)	-B+A-(98+76*5*4*3*2*-1)
6224	10684	1*2+(3+4*(5*6+7)*8)*9+A-B	BA-98*-76+54-32*-1
6225	10685	-1-(-2+3)-(-456+7*(-8-9AB))	-BA+9*(876-5+4+32*-1)
6226	10686	1234+5+678*9A+B	B+A+9*8*(7+6*5)*4+3*2*1
6227	10687	12+3*-45*6-(7+89*A)*-B	BA-98*-76-5*(4+3)*(-2-1)
6228	10688	123-4+5+678*(9-A)*-B	B+A+9+8+(7+6+5+4)^3+2*1
6229	10689	1234-567-8*-9*AB	-B-A*(98-(765+43*2)+1)
622A	10690	1*2345-6*(-789-A)+B	B-A9-(-8-76*5*4*3*2*1)
622B	10691	1+2345+6*(789+A)+B	-B-A-9+876*(5+4)-321
6230	10692	1*(23-4*-56-(-7+89A))*-B	-B*(-A-(98-7)-(654+3*-21))
6231	10693	1+2+3+456+7*(8+9AB)	BA9-8*765+4*3*21
6232	10694	-1-234+5678+9AB	B+A+9*-8-7*(6-(-543*-2-1))
6233	10695	1*-234+5678+9AB	B-A-98*-76-5*43-(2-1)
6234	10696	1-234+5678+9AB	BA+9*-8+7*-6*(-5*43-2) *1
6235	10697	-1+2-34-(-5+67-89*A) *B	B+A+(-9-8)*(7+6+5*-4*3*2-1)
6236	10698	-1-2+3*-4*56*(-7-8)+9*-AB	BA-98*(-76-5+4-3+2+1)
6237	10699	-123-(4+5)-(-6-(-78+9))*-AB	-B-A-9*-876-5+4-321
6238	10700	12-3*-45-(-678+9A) *B	B+A+(9+8+7*6)*(5*4*3^2+1)
6239	10701	123+45-6*78*(-9-A) -B	B+A*(-87+6)+5+4*321
623A	10702	-1+(-2/-3-4*(5-6*7)) *8*9+A-B	BA+9*876-(5+432-1)
623B	10703	-1+2-3+(4+5)*-67-8*-9AB	B+A+(9*(-8+7*6) *-5+4)*(-3*2-1)
6240	10704	-1*(2+3-45)*(-678+9*AB)	B-A98*-7+(-6+54) *3-321
6241	10705	-123-(-45-67*(8+9A+B))	BA9-8+76*5*4*(3+2*1)
6242	10706	12345+6-7-89A*B	-B+A-987*-6-543*(-2-1)
6243	10707	-1+234-5-6+7+8*9A*B	-B-A98*-7+(-6+54) *3*(-2+1)
6244	10708	12345-6-(-7+89A*B)	-B+A98-76+5432-1
6245	10709	(-1-2)*(-3*4^5+6-7*8*9)+A-B	-B+A98-76-5432*-1
6246	10710	-1*(2+3*4-(-5-(67-8))) *(-9+A*-B)	-B+A98-76+5432+1
6247	10711	123-4*5+(67-(-8-9)) *-A*-B	-B+A-9+876*(5+4)-321
6248	10712	-1-2-34*56-(-789A+B)	-B+A-98+7*(6+543*2-1)
6249	10713	1234+5-6*(-7-(8+9AB))	B-(A+9*-876)-(5+4+321)
624A	10714	1+2-34-567+89*-A*-B	-B*(A9+8-765-43+21)
624B	10715	-1+2-3*45-(-6-78*9A)+B	B+A+(-9-8)*(7-(6+5^4+3)-2)+1
6250	10716	-12+3+45*(-6-7)+8*9AB	B+A+(9-8+7^6-5)/(4*3-2+1)
6251	10717	12-3+45*(6-7*-8+9+AB)	B+A+(9+8*(7*6+5^4+3)) *2*1
6252	10718	1+2+34*-56+789A-B	B+A9*(8+7+6+5+4-3+2-1)
6253	10719	-1-2-3*(-4+5)+(-678-(9+A)) *-B	B+A+((-9-8) *7*6*5+4) *3^3(2-1)
6254	10720	12345-(-6-7+89A*B)	-B*A-(9-8+7*6+5*4*3)^2+1
6255	10721	-12-34+5678+9*AB	BA+98*76+54-3*21
6256	10722	12+3*-4*-567-8*(-9-AB)	B-A98*-7+6*5-4*3*2+1
6257	10723	1-(2+3-45*(-6-7)+8*-9AB)	-B-A-(-9-8)*(-7-(6-5)) *(-4+3*-21)
6258	10724	-1-(234+56)-(-789*A+B)	-B+A98-76*(-54-32) -1
6259	10725	-12+3*456+7*(89A-B)	B*(A9-87-65+4*3)*-21
625A	10726	1-234-56+789*A-B	B+A+9+8*-7+6*5*4*(3+21)
625B	10727	-123+4+5678+9A*B	-B+A9-87*(-65-4-(-3+21))
6260	10728	12-3*45+6+78*9A+B	B+A+(-9*-8*7-6) *(5*4+3/2)^1
6261	10729	-1-23+456*-7+89AB	BA9+8*(-765-4-32) *1
6262	10730	123+4*-567+89*AB	B-(-A98-(-76+5432-1))
6263	10731	1-23-(-456*-7-89AB)	B+A98-76+5432*1
6264	10732	-1-(2+34-5678)+9*AB	B+A98-76+5432+1
6265	10733	-1-2+3-45+6+(-7+89) *-A*-B	-BA-98-7-6*(-5+4*-321)
6266	10734	-1-2+34*-56+789A+B	B-A9*(-87+65)+4321
6267	10735	-123+45*-6-78*(9-AB)	B+A+9+8*(7+(6+5)^(4-(3-2))) +1
6268	10736	-1-2345+6-(-7-89) *AB	B*(A+98+76-5*-4*3*2*1)
6269	10737	1*2-34+5678+9*AB	B-A98*-7-6-5*(4-(-3-21))

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
626A	10738	1+2-34+5678-9*-AB	BA-98+7*-6*-5*43+2*1
626B	10739	-1-23-456-7+8*9AB	-BA+987*-6+543*21
6270	10740	-12-3-456*7+89AB	B+A+9*8+(7+6+5+4)^3-2+1
6271	10741	1+2-345+(67+8)*(9A+B)	B-A9*-8-(7+6)*(-543+21)
6272	10742	(1+2+3-4)^5*6*7*8-9+A-B	-B-A*(98+76)*-5-(4-321)
6273	10743	-1-(23+4-5678+9*-AB)	B+A+9*8+(7+6+5+4)^3+2/1
6274	10744	1-2-345+6+78*(-9+AB)	BA9-(87+6+5*-4*321)
6275	10745	1-23-4+5678+9*AB	B+A+(9+8)*7*6*5+4)*3+2*1
6276	10746	123+456+7*(-8+9AB)	B-(A-9*(876+5-43-2))-1
6277	10747	-1-2*-34+(-5-67)*(-8-(9-A*-B))	B+A98+76*(54-32*-1)
6278	10748	12345-(67-89A*-B)	B+A+9+8-7*(6-543)*-2*-1
6279	10749	12345-6*-7+89A*-B	B+A-9*8-76*-5*4*(3+2+1)
627A	10750	-12-3-456-(7+8*-9AB)	-BA-98*7-65*4*32*-1
627B	10751	-1-23+4+5678-9*-AB	-BA+98*-7+65*4*32+1
6280	10752	12*-3*4*(5+67-8-9-AB)	BA-9*8*7+6543-21
6281	10753	-1-23-456-(-7+8*-9AB)	B-A98*-7+6*(-54+32+1)
6282	10754	-12-3-4-(-5678-9*AB)	-B*-A-9+8+(7+6+5+4)^3-2-1
6283	10755	-1+2-3+456*-7+89AB	B+A9*(-8-(76-54))-(-32+1)
6284	10756	-1*(23-4+5*-67-8*9A*B)	-BA-98*-76-(-5-(-4+321))
6285	10757	-1*(-2+3)*(-456*-7-89AB)	-B+A98*7+6+5*(-43+21)
6286	10758	-1-(2-(-34-56)-78*9A)+B	-B*(-A9-876-54+321)
6287	10759	1-23+4-5+6-(7-89)*-A*-B	-B-A+(-9+8/7)*(6+5*-4)^3*2^1-1
6288	10760	1-2-34-(56+78*-9A)+B	B+A+(9+8*(7*6+5^4+3))^2+1
6289	10761	-1+2-(-34+5)+(678+9A)*B	-B+A98*7-65-4-32-1
628A	10762	-12+3+4-5-(6-(7-89)*A*-B)	BA9+8*-7*6*5+4321
628B	10763	1-2-3-456-7-8*-9AB	-B+A98*7-65-4-32+1
6290	10764	-12+3-4-56+78*9A-B	-B-A-9*-876+54-321
6291	10765	1+234*5*6-7*(8-9-AB)	B+A+(9+8)*(7+6+5^4-3*2)^1
6292	10766	1+2*(3+4)-567-89*-A*B	B+A+(-9-(-8-7)*-6*-5*4)*3*2-1
6293	10767	1-(-2+3)-(456+7)+8*9AB	B-A9+8*7*(-6-543)*-2-1
6294	10768	12-3-456*7+89AB	-BA98+7*6*(543-21)
6295	10769	-1+2-3-4-5678-9*AB	BA9-8*-7+6*5*4*3*21
6296	10770	1*-2-3-4-56+78*9A-B	-B-A98*-7-(-65+4-32)*-1
6297	10771	1-(2+3)-4-(56-78*9A)-B	BA9+8-76+5*4*321
6298	10772	1-23-(45-6)-(-78*9A+B)	-BA-9-8-7-6*(5+4*-321)
6299	10773	-1-2-3+4+5678+9*AB	B-A98*-7+(65+43+2)*-1
629A	10774	12+3+456*-7+89AB	B-A98*-7-65-43-2+1
629B	10775	1234+567-8*9*A*-B	-B+A98+76-5*4*-321
62A0	10776	1-234*-56+(-78+9)*AB	BA+9-8+7*(-6+(-54+3)*-21)
62A1	10777	-12+34-(567+89*-A*B)	B-A9+8*(76-543)*-2-1
62A2	10778	12-(3+456+78*-9AB)	-B+A987-(-65+43-21)
62A3	10779	-1-234-5-6-(-789*A+B)	-B-A*(-98-7-654-3-21)
62A4	10780	1*-2*(-3-45-6*78+9A)*B	BA+9*(876-54-(-3-2)-1)
62A5	10781	1+2*3-4*567-89A*-B	B-A9*(8-76-5)+4-321
62A6	10782	12-3-4+5678-9*-AB	-BA+9*876-5*43+2-1
62A7	10783	-1-23-(-4+56)-(-78-9)*-AB	-B-A-98-7*6*5*(-43-2+1)
62A8	10784	123-4-567+8*9AB	B+A-9*-8*((7*6+5)*-4-3/-2)-1
62A9	10785	-1-(-2-3)-456-(7+8*9AB))	-B-(-A98+7)-(-6-5432)-1
62AA	10786	-12+3-(4+56+78*-9A-B)	-B+A98-(7+6)+5432*1
62AB	10787	1-(-2-3)-456+7-8*-9AB	-B+A+98*(76+5-4+3-(2-1))
62B0	10788	1-(2-3+4+5+6)-(-78*9A+B)	BA-(-987+6-5432)-1
62B1	10789	-12-34-5*6-(-78+9)*AB	BA+987-(6+5432*-1)
62B2	10790	12-3+4+5678-9*-AB	BA+987-6+5432+1
62B3	10791	12+3+4*-567+89A*B	-B*(-A9-(-8+76+543-2+1))
62B4	10792	123+4-567-8*-9AB	-BA*(-9-87-(-65+4+32)+1)
62B5	10793	-1234+5+6+(7-89)*-AB	BA+987-6*543*2*-1
62B6	10794	12-3+4-56+78*9A-B	-B+A+98*76-5*(4-3*21)
62B7	10795	-1-2-3-(45*6+789*-A)-B	B-A98*-7-(6+54+32*1)
62B8	10796	-1+2*(34-5)*6-7+8*9A*B	-B+A-(-9-8-7*65*-4*(-3+2*-1))
62B9	10797	-1+23-4+5678+9*AB	-B+A98-(7-6-(5432-1))
62BA	10798	12+3-456+7-8*-9AB	-B-(-A98+7-6)-5432*-1
62BB	10799	1+23-4+5678+9*AB	-B+A98+7-6+5432-1
6300	10800	1*2*-3*(-4-5)*(67-8+9A+B)	BA+987-(-6-5432+1)
6301	10801	-12+34-(-5678-9*AB)	BA+987+6+5432*1
6302	10802	12-34+5-67*(-8-9A-B)	BA-(-987-6)+5432+1
6303	10803	-1-2-34-(-5-6)-78*-9A-B	BA9-8*7+6-5*4*-321
6304	10804	12+345-67+8*9A*B	B+A+98*76+(5+4)*32+1
6305	10805	12+34-(567+89*A*-B)	-B-A+98-7*(-6+543)*2*-1
6306	10806	-12+34-(5-(-678-9A))*-B	-B-A98*-7+65+4*-32*1
6307	10807	-1-(-23+456-7)-8*-9AB	B+A98-7-6+5432-1
6308	10808	12-3-4-56+78*9A+B	B+A98-7-6-5432*-1
6309	10809	1+23-456+7-8*-9AB	B+A98-7-6+5432+1
630A	10810	-1-23-(-4+5)-6+78*-9A+B)	-B+A98*7-6-54-3-2*-1
630B	10811	-1-(234-5)-6+789*-A-B)	-B+A98-(-7-6)+5432-1
6310	10812	-1+2-3-(-4-5*6-(7-89)*A*-B)	B+A98-(7+6*-543*2*1)
6311	10813	-1234-5-6+78*(9+AB)	-B+A98+7+6+5432+1
6312	10814	-12-34-5+6-78*-9A+B	-B+A987-65*43*-2*-1
6313	10815	-1-(23+4*-5)+67*(8+9A+B)	B+A+9*876-54*(3+2+1)
6314	10816	-1+2+34-(-5678+9*-AB)	B+A+(9+8)*(7+6*5*4)*(3+2)*1
6315	10817	12345+6*(-78-9A)*B	B+A+(9+8)*(7+6*5*4)*(3+2)+1
6316	10818	1+2-(-34-5678-9*AB)	B-A+9+8-76*5*-4*3*-2*-1
6317	10819	-123+4*-5*6+(-78-9)*A*-B	B+A98-(7-6)-(-5432+1)
6318	10820	-12+345-67*(8-9)*AB	B+A98-7+6-5432*-1
6319	10821	-12-3+4-5-(6+78*-9A+B)	B+A98+7-6+5432-1
631A	10822	12*(3+456+7-8+9A+B)	B+A98+7-6-5432*-1
631B	10823	-1-(2+34)+5-(6-(78*9A+B))	-B+A-(-98*76+54*-3*2*1)
6320	10824	1*-234*(-56+7-89+AB)	-B+A+987*6+54*32-1
6321	10825	-1-2-(3-4*-5)-(-6+78*-9A+B)	B-A98*-7+(-65+43)*(-2+1)
6322	10826	1-23*4+56-(78*-9A-B)	BA-98+76*5*-4*-3*2*-1
6323	10827	-12+34-(56+78*-9A-B)	BA-98*-76-5*(-43+2)*1
6324	10828	1*2*(-3+45*(-6-(7-89-A)))+B)	B+A98*7+6-5-43-21

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6325	10829	$-12 - (-3 - (-4+5) - (-6+78*9A-B))$	$-B-A9+8*-76*-5+4321$
6326	10830	$(-1 - (-2-3+4*5)*6)*-7*(8+9) - (A-B)$	$-BA-98*(-76-5)-43+2+1$
6327	10831	$1 - (-2+3+4+5+6)+78*9A+B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)*6*5*4*3*2+1$
6328	10832	$1+2+3-4+5+6+(78-9)*AB$	$B-A9+(-8+76+54)*-3*-21$
6329	10833	$12+34-56+78*9A-B$	$B+A98+7+6+5432-1$
632A	10834	$-1 - (-23+45+6+78*-9A)+B$	$B-A-98*-76-(54-321)$
632B	10835	$-1234+5+6-78*(-9-AB)$	$B+A987-65*-43*-2-1$
6330	10836	$1+23-45-(6-78*9A)+B$	$B+A987-65*-43*2*-1$
6331	10837	$1+2+345-67*(-8+9)*-AB$	$-B+A98*7-(65+4-(32-1))$
6332	10838	$-12-345-67-8*-9AB$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6*5+4^3)^2+1$
6333	10839	$-1 - (-2+34)+5 - (-6 - (-78*-9A+B))$	$B+A-9*8*(7*(-6-5/4)^3+2)^{\wedge}1$
6334	10840	$-12 - (34-5678+9A*-B)$	$-B - (-A98-7*6) - (-5432+1)$
6335	10841	$-12+3456-7*-8*-9*-A-B$	$BA+987*6+5*(4+321)$
6336	10842	$123-4+5*(678+9*AB)$	$B+A+9+(8-7*6)*(-5*4^3+2)^{\wedge}1$
6337	10843	$-12-3*4*(5-6)+78*9A-B$	$BA-9*-876 - (-5*-4+321)$
6338	10844	$1 - (-2-3) - 4 - 56* - 7+8*-9A*-B$	$-B-A98*-7-(6+5)-(43-21)$
6339	10845	$-1-23*4+56*-7+8*9AB$	$B+A+9+(8^{\wedge}(7-6)*-5-4^3)^2-2-1$
633A	10846	$1-23+4-5+6-78*-9A+B$	$-BA9-(8-7654+321)$
633B	10847	$1+23+4-(5*6-78*9A+B)$	$BA+9-8*7+6*54*(-3-21)$
6340	10848	$-123-4+5678+9AB$	$B+A+987*6+54*32+1$
6341	10849	$12-3 - (-4+5+6) - (78*-9A+B)$	$-BA-98-(7-6543+21)$
6342	10850	$12*(-345-6 - (-7-89A+B))$	$-B+A98*7+6 - (-5+4+32*1)$
6343	10851	$-12-345+6789-AB$	$B-A98*-7+6+5*4*-3+2*1$
6344	10852	$12-345*6-(7-89*AB)$	$B+A98*7-65 - (-43+21)$
6345	10853	$-1 - (-2 - (-345-67-8*-9AB))$	$B+A*(9-8)*(765-(4-3))^2+1$
6346	10854	$-12+345+6-7+8*-9A*-B$	$B-A9-8-76*(-5+3)*2*1$
6347	10855	$1234-56-7*(89+A)*-B$	$-B-A98*7*(-6+5)-(43-21)$
6348	10856	$-123+4+5678+9AB$	$B+A-9*-8*-7*(6-5*(4+3/2))-1$
6349	10857	$1 - (-2+34-5678+9A*-B)$	$BA9-87-(6-(5432-1))$
634A	10858	$1 - (-2-3) - 4 - (5+6)+78*9A+B$	$BA9-8+7+6*5*4*-321$
634B	10859	$1+23+4*-5+6+78*9A-B$	$BA9-87-6+5432+1$
6350	10860	$-12 - (-3+4+5*-6-78*9A)-B$	$-BA-9-87+6543-21$
6351	10861	$12-3+4-56*-7-8*9A*-B$	$BA9-87-6*-543*2-1$
6352	10862	$-1-2-345+6789-AB$	$-BA9+8+7654-321$
6353	10863	$1*-2-(345-6789+AB)$	$-BA-98 - (-7-6543) - 21$
6354	10864	$1-2-345 - (-6789+AB)$	$B+A98*(-7-6)+5432+1$
6355	10865	$-12-3 - (-4-5-6+78*-9A-B)$	$B-A9-8-7+6*(5+4*321)$
6356	10866	$-1+2-345+6789-AB$	$-BA+9+8-7+6*(5-4*-321)$
6357	10867	$1-2+345 - (-6+7-8*-9A*-B)$	$B+A98*7 - (-6+54+3)+21$
6358	10868	$1+2-345+6789-AB$	$BA9-8-76+5432-1$
6359	10869	$-1+2*-3*-4+56*7-8*9A*-B$	$BA9-87+6+5432-1$
635A	10870	$-12+34+5-6-78*-9A-B$	$BA9-8-(76-5432-1)$
635B	10871	$-1 - (2-3) - 4 - (5*6 - (-78*-9A-B))$	$-B-A9-87+6543-21$
6360	10872	$1+2 - (3 - (4-5+6) - 78*9A)+B$	$B+A+(9+8)*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4)+3+2*1$
6361	10873	$-1 - (23+456+7-89*-A*-B)$	$-BA-(98+7)+6543-(2-1)$
6362	10874	$-1+23+4 - (-5+6) - 78*-9A-B$	$B+A98*7-(65-43)-2-1$
6363	10875	$12-3-4-5+6 - (-78*9A-B)$	$-BA-98-(7-6543) - (-2+1)$
6364	10876	$-1 - (-2-3-4+5-6+78*-9A-B)$	$-BA-98-7+6543+2*1$
6365	10877	$1-23*4*-5*(6-7)-8*-9AB$	$-BA-98-7+6543+2+1$
6366	10878	$-12*(-3 - (-45+678-9A-B))$	$-BA - (-9+87) - (-6543+21)$
6367	10879	$12 - (345-6789+AB)$	$B*(-A+9+876+5*-43+2+1)$
6368	10880	$-1 - (-2-3) - (-4-5+6+(78-9)*-AB)$	$-BA+9*(876-5-4)+3*-21$
6369	10881	$-12 - (-3-45+6)+78*9A-B$	$-B+A98*(-76-5+43*-2*-1)$
636A	10882	$12 - (-345-6+7)+8*9A*B$	$-BA-(9+87-6543 - (-2-1))$
636B	10883	$1+23-4*56 - (-789*A+B)$	$-BA-9-87+6543+2*-1$
6370	10884	$-1-2-3-4+5678-9A*-B$	$BA9+8-76+5432-1$
6371	10885	$-12-3*4+56-78*-9A-B$	$BA9-(8-76*(54+32)*1)$
6372	10886	$1-234-5-6+78*(-9+AB)$	$-BA-98+7+6543-2*1$
6373	10887	$-1+2-345+6789-A*B$	$-BA-98*7 - (-6543+2)+1$
6374	10888	$12+34-5-6+78*9A-B$	$-B - (-A98-76-5432+1)$
6375	10889	$1+2-345+6789-A*B$	$-B+A98*76-5432*-1$
6376	10890	$1 - (-2+3+4-5678+9A*-B)$	$-B+A98 - (-76-5432-1)$
6377	10891	$12-3-4+5+6+(-78+9)*-AB$	$-BA-98+7 - (-6543-(2+1))$
6378	10892	$-12*(34-5-6-78*9A+B)$	$B+A+9*8*7+6^{\wedge}5*4/3-2+1$
6379	10893	$-123+45*-67+89AB$	$B-(A9+87-(6543-21))$
637A	10894	$-1+2 - (-3 - (-4+5678+9A*B))$	$B-A*-9+(8-7+6)*543*2-1$
637B	10895	$-1-2 - (3+456+7)-89*-A*B$	$-B-(A9+87-(6543-2))+1$
6380	10896	$12+345+6+7-8*9A*-B$	$B+A*(9-8)*765-(4-32-1)$
6381	10897	$-12-3+45-6 - (-78*9A-B)$	$-B-A9-87+6543+2-1$
6382	10898	$1-234-5+6-78*(9-AB)$	$-B+A*987-6-5*(432+1)$
6383	10899	$-1+2-3-456-(7-89*-A*-B)$	$-BA-98-7+6543+21$
6384	10900	$-1234-567+89*AB$	$-BA+9-87+6543-(2+1)$
6385	10901	$12-3-4+5678+9A*B$	$B*(A9-87+654 - (-32+1))$
6386	10902	$-1+2+3+4+5678-9A*-B$	$B+A - (-987*-6-543*21)$
6387	10903	$-1-2+34+5-6-78*-9A+B$	$-BA+9+(87-6543)*(-2+1)$
6388	10904	$123-45+6+(7-89)*-A*B$	$B+A98*7 - (-6-5+4-3*2*-1)$
6389	10905	$-1 - (-2+3 - (-4+56-78*-9A-B))$	$B+A98*7-6+5+4-3-2*-1$
638A	10906	$12345+67+89A*-B$	$-BA+9-87+6543+2+1$
638B	10907	$-1+2+34+5-6-78*-9A+B$	$-B+A98*7*(6-5)+43-21$
6390	10908	$1*23*4*(5-6)*(78+9)*(A-B)$	$-BA+9*8*(76+54)-32*1$
6391	10909	$12345-6-7+89*-AB$	$-B-A98*-7+65-43-2*-1$
6392	10910	$1+2+3+45 - (-6-78*9A)-B$	$B+A98 - (-76-5432+1)$
6393	10911	$-123-45-6+789*A+B$	$B+A98+76+5432*1$
6394	10912	$-12 - (3+4-56) - (-78*9A-B)$	$B+A98+76+5432+1$
6395	10913	$1+2+3-4+56-78*-9A-B$	$-B+A98*7+6 - (-54+32)*1$
6396	10914	$-1+23*-4+5678+9AB$	$B+A+9-8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+4)/(3+2/1)$
6397	10915	$12 - (3-45-6) - (-78*9A+B)$	$B-A9-87+6543-2-1$
6398	10916	$-1-23*45+6*(-7+89)*(A+B)$	$-B+A9*(8+7+6+54)+32*-1$
6399	10917	$1-2-345-(6+7)-8*-9AB$	$-BA-98*-76 - (-5-432*1)$
639A	10918	$-12 - (345+6 - (78*9AB))$	$-B-A9*-87+6*(54-321)$
639B	10919	$-1+23*4*-5+6789-A-B$	$-B+A98*7+6-5+4*3+21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
63A0	10920	$1+23+45-(6+78^*-9A)-B$	$B-A9-87-(-6543-2)^*1$
63A1	10921	$-123+4+56^*-7+89^*A^*B$	$-B-A9-87+6543+21$
63A2	10922	$-123+4-5-(-6+78)^*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A98^*7-(-6+5)^*4+32-1$
63A3	10923	$-1^*(-23+4+5-678-9A)^*B$	$B-A-9^*-876-54^*(3+2-1)$
63A4	10924	$1234-5-6+7^*89A-B$	$-B+A98^*7+65-(-4+32)^*1$
63A5	10925	$12-3-(-45+6+78^*-9A-B)$	$-B+A98^*7+65-(-4+32)+1$
63A6	10926	$12-3+4+56-78^*-9A-B$	$B+A+9-8^*(7-(6^*5+4+3)^2)^{1/2}$
63A7	10927	$1+23-4+5^*6+(-78+9)^*-AB$	$-B-A98^*-7+6+5-4+32+1$
63A8	10928	$123+456^*-7+89AB$	$-BA+9-87-(-6543-21)$
63A9	10929	$-1-(2+345)-(6-7+8^*-9AB)$	$-B-A-98^*-76-5^*-43^*2^*1$
63AA	10930	$-12-345-(-6-7-8^*9AB)$	$B+A98^*7+6-5+43-21$
63AB	10931	$-1-2+34+5678-9A^*-B$	$-BA-9^*8+7+6543-2+1$
63B0	10932	$12+34-(-5-6)-(-78^*9A-B)$	$-B+A98^*7+65-43+21$
63B1	10933	$1-2-3+4+56-(-78^*9A-B)$	$-BA-9^*-876-54-32-1$
63B2	10934	$12^*(-34-(-5-67)-(89+A))^*-B$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(-87-(654-32+1))$
63B3	10935	$-1+2-(-34-5678)-9A^*-B$	$BA9-8-(-76-5^*-4^*-321)$
63B4	10936	$1+23+(-4-5)^*(-6+78-9A^*B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7+6-5^*4^3)^*2+1$
63B5	10937	$1+2+34+5678-9A^*-B$	$-B-A98^*-7-6^*-5+43-21$
63B6	10938	$123-(456+7-8^*9AB)$	$-B-A^*9-87+6543+2+1$
63B7	10939	$1-(2-(-3+4+56)-(-78-9)^*AB)$	$-B-A-9+8^*76^*5+4321$
63B8	10940	$-1^*-2^*(-3-(-456+78))^*(9-A+B)$	$-B-(A-98^*76-54-321)$
63B9	10941	$1-2-3^*4+56^*-7-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A9+8^*-7+6543-2^*1$
63BA	10942	$123-4+5678+9^*AB$	$B-A98^*-7-(6+5)-(-43-(-2+1))$
63BB	10943	$-1-2^*3-4+56^*-7-8^*-9AB$	$-BA+9^*-8-7+6543+21$
6400	10944	$-1+234-567+8^*9AB$	$-BA-9^*-876-54-3-21$
6401	10945	$123-4^*567+89A^*B$	$B-A^*9+8^*(7+654+321)$
6402	10946	$1234-(5+6)-7^*-89A+B$	$BA9-8-7-6+5432^*1$
6403	10947	$1+2-(-345-6-7-8^*9AB)$	$-BA-(-9-8^*-7-6543)-2-1$
6404	10948	$12+34+5678-9A^*-B$	$-BA-9-8-(-7-6543+21)$
6405	10949	$-1+2+345+67-8^*-9A^*B$	$-B+A98^*7-(-65+4+3+2)^*1$
6406	10950	$123+4+5678-9^*-AB$	$BA9+87-6-5^*4^*-321$
6407	10951	$1+2-(-345-67+8^*9A^*-B)$	$BA+9-8^*76^*-5^*(4-(3-2))^*1$
6408	10952	$123-456+7-8^*-9AB$	$-BA-9^*-876-(5+4-3^*-21)$
6409	10953	$-1+234^*-5^*-6-(-789+A-B)$	$-B+A-98+(-7-6-5)^*(-432-1)$
640A	10954	$1+23+45+6-78^*-9A+B$	$B-A98^*-7+65-(43-21)$
640B	10955	$-123-4-5-6+789^*A+B$	$-BA+9^*-8^*(-76-54)+3^*(2+1)$
6410	10956	$1234+5-6-7^*-89A+B$	$B-A98^*-7-(-6-5-(4+32))^*1$
6411	10957	$(-1+2^*3^*-4)^*(-5-6^*7^*8+9)-(A-B)$	$-B+A98^*7+6+5+3+2+1$
6412	10958	$-1+2^*345+(-6+7-8)^*-9AB$	$B+A^*-9-87-(-6543-2)-1$
6413	10959	$-12-(-345-6^*7)-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A9-8-7+6543-21$
6414	10960	$-1+(-2-3^*4^*-5)^*(-6-7-8)^*-9A+B$	$BA-(-9-8+76^*-5^*4^3+2-1)$
6415	10961	$-12-345-(-6789-(-A-B))$	$BA9+8-(7+6)-(-5432+1)$
6416	10962	$1-2+3+4^*-56+78^*(-9+AB)$	$BA9+8-7-6+5432^*1$
6417	10963	$12345-67-89^*AB$	$BA9+8-7-(6-5432-1)$
6418	10964	$12345-6^*-7-89^*AB$	$-BA-9-(-8+7-6543+21)$
6419	10965	$12-(-34-56-78^*9A+B)$	$-B-A9^*-87-(6-5^*(-4-321))$
641A	10966	$-123+4^*56-(-78-9)^*-AB$	$-BA+9-8-7-(-6543+21)$
641B	10967	$12+3-4-56^*7+8^*9AB$	$BA98+7^*(6-5-4)^*321$
6420	10968	$1+23^*-4-56+789^*A+B$	$-B-(A9+8^*7)-(-6543-21)$
6421	10969	$-12-34+5678+9AB$	$B+A+9^*876-5^*43+21$
6422	10970	$((-1-2^*3^*4^5)/-6+7)^*8-9A+B$	$-BA-9^*-876-54-(3-2+1)$
6423	10971	$-1^*(2-34-56+78^*-9A-B)$	$-BA-9^*-876-54^*(3-2)-1$
6424	10972	$-1-2-345-(-6789+A+B)$	$-BA-9-8-7+6543-2+1$
6425	10973	$-1^*(2+345-6789+A+B)$	$-B-A9-8+7+6543-21$
6426	10974	$1-2-345+6789-A-B$	$BA9+8-7+6+5432^*1$
6427	10975	$1^*2+34+56-78^*-9A+B$	$-BA+9+8^*-7+6543+21$
6428	10976	$-1+2-345-(-6789-(-A-B))$	$BA9+8+7-6+5432^*1$
6429	10977	$-1+2^*(3-(-4+56))^*-78-9+AB$	$BA9+8+7-(6-5432-1)$
642A	10978	$1+2-345+6789-A-B$	$-B^*(A-(-9-(-8-765-(-43-21))))$
642B	10979	$-1+2-3-4-(-5-6-78)^*9A+B$	$B+A98^*7+65-(-4-(3^*-2+1))$
6430	10980	$-1-2-34+5678+9AB$	$-BA+9-(-8-7-6543)-21$
6431	10981	$-12-345+6789+A-B$	$B-A9-8-7-(-6543+21)$
6432	10982	$1-2-34-(-5678-9AB)$	$-BA-(-9-8)-7+6543-21$
6433	10983	$-12-345+6789-A+B$	$-B-(A9+8)-7-(-6543+2-1)$
6434	10984	$-1+2-(-34-5678)+9AB$	$-B-(A+98)+7+6543-21$
6435	10985	$12+3^*45^*(-67+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A9-8-7+6543+2-1$
6436	10986	$1+2-34+5678+9AB$	$-BA-9+8-(-7-6543+2+1)$
6437	10987	$-1+2-345-67+89^*-A^*-B$	$BA9-(-8-7)-(-6-5432+1)$
6438	10988	$-123-4^*56+7+8^*9AB$	$-BA-(-9+8)-(-7-6543-(-2-1))$
6439	10989	$12-345+6789-A-B$	$B^*(-A-9-(8+7)-65)^*(-4-3-2^*1)$
643A	10990	$12^*(-34+567-(89-AB))$	$-B+A-98-7+6543-21$
643B	10991	$-1-23-4-(-5678-9AB)$	$-BA-9+8-7+6543+2^*1$
6440	10992	$-1-2-345+6789+A-B$	$B+A+98^*(76+5)+43-2)^*-1$
6441	10993	$1-23-4+5678+9AB$	$B-A98^*-7-6^*-5^*(4-3)^*(2+1)$
6442	10994	$1-2-345+6789+A-B$	$-BA+9-8-7+6543+2+1$
6443	10995	$1+2^*(3-4-5^*-6^*-7)+8^*9AB$	$-B+A98^*7+6^*-5^*-4+3^*-2^*1$
6444	10996	$1-(2+345)-(-6789+A-B)$	$-B-A9-(8-7)-(-6543-2^*-1)$
6445	10997	$12-34+5678+9AB$	$-B-A9-8+7+6543-2+1$
6446	10998	$1+2-345+6789+A-B$	$-BA-(9+8+7-6543-21)$
6447	10999	$-1-23+4+5678+9AB$	$-B-A+9-(87-6543)-21$
6448	11000	$1+2-345+6789-A+B$	$-B-(A98-7654)-321$
6449	11001	$1-23-(-4-(5678+9AB))$	$-BA-9+8+7+6543-2^*1$
644A	11002	$-12-3-(-4-5678-9AB)$	$-BA-(-9+8-7)-(-6543+2+1)$
644B	11003	$-12-345+6789+A+B$	$B-A-9-87-(-6543+21)$
6450	11004	$-1-2-3^*4^*-567-8+9AB$	$-BA-9+8+7+6543+2-1$
6451	11005	$1-234-5-67+8^*9AB$	$-B-A-9-87+6543-2+1$
6452	11006	$-123-45+6-78^*(9-AB)$	$-BA+9-8+7+6543+2-1$
6453	11007	$1-(-2+3^*(4+56+7-89)^*AB)$	$-BA+9-(8-7)+6543+2^*1$
6454	11008	$-12+3-4+5678+9AB$	$BA9-8^*-765+432+1$
6455	11009	$12-345+6789+A-B$	$-B-A9-8-7+6543+21$
6456	11010	$-12-3-(-4-5678-9AB)$	$B+A9-(8+7^*(-6-543))^*-2^*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6457	11011	12-345+6789-A+B	-B-A9+8+7+6543-(2+1)
6458	11012	12+3*(4+5*6)*(7-8-(9+AB))	-B+A-98-7+6543-2-1
6459	11013	-1-(2+3)-4+5678+9AB	-B+A-98-7*-6*5*(-43-2)*-1
645A	11014	-1+2*-3*-4*-56*7-(8*9-(A-B))	-BA-9+8-7+6543+21
645B	11015	1-2-(3+4)-(-5678-9AB)	B-A-(98+7)-(6543-2)*-1
6460	11016	-1-234-(5-(6789-AB))	-B-A9+8+7+6543-2*-1
6461	11017	-1+2-3-4+5678+9AB	B-A9-8+7-(6543+2)-1
6462	11018	1*2-3-4+5678+9AB	B-A9-8+7+6543+2*-1
6463	11019	1-(-2+3+4-5678-9AB)	-B+A+9-87+6543-21
6464	11020	1*-2-(-3+4)-(-5678-9AB)	B-A-98-7+6543+2+1
6465	11021	1-2+3-4+5678+9AB	B-A+9-(87-6543+21)
6466	11022	-12-(-3-456-7)-8*9A*-B	B-A98+7654-321
6467	11023	1-2-3+4+5678+9AB	B-(A-(9-87)-(6543-21))
6468	11024	12-(345-67-8*9AB)	-BA-(9-8)-(-7-6543)+2+1
6469	11025	-1+2-(3-4-(5678+9AB))	B-A9-(8+7)-(-6543-2)+1
646A	11026	-1-234+5-(-6789+AB)	-B-A+9-87+6543-2*-1
646B	11027	-1-2+3+4+5678+9AB	-B-A-(9+87-6543-2)+1
6470	11028	1-234+5-(-6789+AB)	B-A-98+7+6543-2-1
6471	11029	1-2+3-(-4-5678)+9AB	B+A98*7-6*-5*4+3*2*1
6472	11030	1-(234+56-7+8*-9AB)	-BA+9-8+7+6543+21
6473	11031	12-345+6789+A+B	-B-A-(9+87)+6543+21
6474	11032	12*(-34-56*7-8+9A*B)	-BA+9*876-5-4+3+2*1
6475	11033	1+2+3+4-(-5678-9AB)	-BA-9*876*(-5+4)+3*(-2+1)
6476	11034	1-2+3*4+5678+9AB	-B-A-(98-7-6543-21)
6477	11035	-1-2-3-45+(-6+78)*(9A+B)	B-A9-(8-7-(6543-2))+1
6478	11036	12+3-(4-(5678+9AB))	B+A-98-7-(6543+2)+1
6479	11037	-1-(234-(-5+6789-A*B))	B+A-98-7-6543*(-2+1)
647A	11038	1-23-45*67+89AB	B+A-98-7-(-6543-2+1)
647B	11039	1-234-(5-6789)-A*B	B-A9-(8-7)+6543-(-2-1)
6480	11040	-1*(-23-45)*(-6+7+8-(-9A-B))	-B-(A-98-(-7+6543+21))
6481	11041	-1+2+3*-4*(-567+8-(9A+B))	B+A+9-87+6543-21
6482	11042	-123-4*5*6*7*8-9AB	B-A-98-(7-6543)+21
6483	11043	123+4-(5-6)-78*-9A+B	-B+A+9-(87-(6543-2))+1
6484	11044	12-3+456+7-8*-9A*B	B-A+9-(87-6543-2*-1)
6485	11045	123-4+5+6+7*8*9A+B	B-A9-8+7+6543+21
6486	11046	-12*(-3+456+7-8-9AB)	-BA-(9-8-7)-(-6543-21)
6487	11047	1+23-4-(-5678-9AB)	B-(A9+8+7)-(-6543-21)
6488	11048	-123-4+5-6+7*8*(-9+AB)	BA9-8+76+5432-1
6489	11049	-12+34-(-5678-9AB)	BA9-(8-76)+5432*1
648A	11050	-1-234+5*6-7+8*9AB	BA9-8+76+5432+1
648B	11051	1-2-(-3+4)-(56+789*-A+B)	B-A*-9+(8-76-54)*-3*21
6490	11052	-12-345-6+7+89*A*B	B+A98*7-65*4+321
6491	11053	-1+23+4+5678+9AB	B+A-98+7+6543-2*-1
6492	11054	1*23+4+5678+9AB	-B+A-98+7+6543+21
6493	11055	12+3*-4-56-789*-A-B	B*(-A-(-98+7-654-(3-21)))
6494	11056	1*23-4*5*6*-78*(-9+A)-B	-B-A-9*-876-54-32+1
6495	11057	-1-2+3+4-56-789*-A-B	-B+A-(9*8+7)+6543+2*-1
6496	11058	-1-2-3-45*67+89AB	-B+A+98*76-(-5-432*1)
6497	11059	-1+23+456-(-7+8*9A*-B)	-BA9-87*(-6-5-43)*2*1
6498	11060	-1-2+34+5678+9AB	-B+A98*7+65+43*2*-1
6499	11061	123-4+5678-9A*-B	B-(A9-8)+7+6543+21
649A	11062	1-2+34-(-5678-9AB)	B+A-98-7+6543+21
649B	11063	-12-3-4*(5+67)-8*-9AB	BA9+87-(6-5432)-1
64A0	11064	-1+2+34+5678+9AB	BA9-(8-76)+5432-1
64A1	11065	-1*(-2-34-5678-9AB)	BA9+87-6+5432+1
64A2	11066	1+2+34+5678+9AB	BA9+8-(-76-5432-1)
64A3	11067	1-2-(3+4+56)-789*-A+B	B+A+9-87+6543+2-1
64A4	11068	1-23-(45-6+789*-A)+B	BA9+87+6*-543*2*-1
64A5	11069	123+4+5678-9A*-B	-B-A-9-8-7+6543-21
64A6	11070	1+2+3-45*67+89AB	-B-(A+9*(-876+5))-4+32*-1
64A7	11071	123+4*5*6*7*8-9-AB	B-A+9-87+6543+21
64A8	11072	123-456-7+89*A*B	-BA+9*876+54-3-21
64A9	11073	1-2-(-3+4+56+789*-A-B)	-B-(A-9*876)-5-(4+3*21)
64AA	11074	-1-2+3-4*5+(-6-78)*(9A-B)	-B+A-(-9*876+54)-(-32+1)
64AB	11075	12-3+45*-67+89AB	BA9+87+6+5432-1
64B0	11076	-12-34-5-6+789*A+B	BA9+87+6+5432*1
64B1	11077	12+34+5678+9AB	BA9+87+6+5432+1
64B2	11078	123-(4-(56+78*9A)+B)	-BA-9*-876+54+3-21
64B3	11079	-1-234+5-(6+7+8*-9AB)	B-A9-(8*-7-(6543+2)*1)
64B4	11080	-12+3-(-45*-6+7+8*-9AB)	-B-A9-8*-7-(6543-21)
64B5	11081	12+345*-6+7-89A*-B	-BA+98-(7-6543)-21
64B6	11082	12-(34-(-5-6-(-789*A+B)))	B+A-9*(-8+765+4*32)*-1
64B7	11083	12-(3+45-6)+789*A-B	-B-A-9-8+7+6543-21
64B8	11084	1-(-2-(-3-4*5-6)-(78+9)*-A*-B)	-BA+9+87+6543-21
64B9	11085	-1-2-3+45*-6-7-8*-9AB	-B-A-9+8-7+6543-21
64BA	11086	-1*(-23+4)*(-567+89A+B)	-B-A-9*-876+5-43-21
64BB	11087	1-(2+3-45*-6+7+8*-9AB)	B-A-(9*-876+54+3)-21
6500	11088	-12+3-(-45-678)*(-9A)*B	B+A-(-9-8*-7)-(-6543+21)
6501	11089	12-(-345-6-7*8*9*(A+B))	-B+A-9-8-7+6543-21
6502	11090	-1+23-45*67+89AB	-BA-(9-87-6543)-(-2-1)
6503	11091	-1*(-23+45*67-89AB)	B+A+9-87+6543+21
6504	11092	1+23+45*-67+89AB	-BA-9+87+6543+2-1
6505	11093	1234-5*67+8*-9*-AB	B-(A+9*-876)-(-5+43*2)+1
6506	11094	-1-(-2+34)-(-5-(6+7)*-8*(-9A+B))	-BA-9+87+6543+2+1
6507	11095	-123-4-5*(-678+9A*-B)	-B+A+98*(76+5)-(-43-21)
6508	11096	1+234*(5-6)+7+8*9AB	-B-A-(9-8*-7)-(-6543-21)
6509	11097	-1+23-4-56-789*-A+B	B+A-9*8+7+6543+2*1
650A	11098	1+2-(3+4)*(-56-78-9AB)	-B+A-9+8*-7+6543+21
650B	11099	1*23-(45-6-789*A)-B	-B-A-9*-876+(5+43+2)*-1
6510	11100	-1*(-2-3+4-(-5+67))*(-8+9+AB)	-B-A-9*-876-5-43-2+1
6511	11101	-12+34-(56+789*-A-B)	-BA+9*8+7+6543+21

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6512	11102	$-12*(345-6-7+(-89-A)*B)$	$-BA-9*-876-5-4-3*-21$
6513	11103	$-1+23-45*(-67-(8-(9-AB)))$	$-BA+98-7+6543-2-1$
6514	11104	$1+234+56789*AB$	$-BA-(-98+7-6543-2*-1)$
6515	11105	$1-2-345+6789A*B$	$-B+A-(9-8)-(7-6543+21)$
6516	11106	$-1+2-(3+4*(-5-6)*-7)+8*9AB$	$-BA+9+87+6543-2-1$
6517	11107	$1+23+4-56+789*A+B$	$-BA+9-(87-(-6543+2))*-1$
6518	11108	$-1*(-2-(-345+6789)-A*B)$	$-BA+9+87+6543-2+1$
6519	11109	$-1-(2+34-5-6-789*A)+B$	$-BA+98-7+6543+2+1$
651A	11110	$1+2+3-4-5-6-789*-A-B$	$-B-A+9-(8-(-7+6543))-2*-1$
651B	11111	$1+2*3-4-5-(6-789*A+B)$	$-BA+9+8*7*(-65-4*32)*-1$
6520	11112	$-1-2-(-34+56)-(789*-A-B)$	$-BA-(-9-87)-(-6543-2-1)$
6521	11113	$-12-345-(-6789-AB)$	$-B-A-(-9-(-8-7-(-6543-2))-1))$
6522	11114	$-12+34+56*7+89*A*B$	$B-A+9*876-(54+3)-2*-1$
6523	11115	$-123*(-45+6-(-7-89))*(A-B)$	$-B+A*9-87+6543*(2-1)$
6524	11116	$1*-2*(-3-4)*(567-(-89+A*B))$	$-BA-9+87+6543+21$
6525	11117	$((1+2+3+4)^5+6+7*8)/9+A-B$	$-BA+98+7+6543-2-1$
6526	11118	$1+2+34-56-789*-A+B$	$B-A-9-8-7-(-6543-2)*1$
6527	11119	$-1-2+34*-56+7-89*-AB$	$-BA-(-98-7)+6543-(2-1)$
6528	11120	$12-345+6789A*B$	$B+A-9-8*7-(-6543-21)$
6529	11121	$12345+67-89*AB$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8-7-6543+2+1)$
652A	11122	$1-2-(3+4)+5+6-789*-A-B$	$B-A-(9*-876-5*-4)-(32-1)$
652B	11123	$-123+4+56-78*(9-AB)$	$B-A+9+87+6543-2+1$
6530	11124	$-1-(2+345)-(-6789-AB)$	$B-A+9+87+6543*(2-1)$
6531	11125	$-12+3*(-45+6)*(-7-8*9*(-A+B))$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8-7-6543)-(-2+1)$
6532	11126	$-123-45+6789-AB$	$-B-A*9+87*(65+4+3+21)$
6533	11127	$-1-2*(3+4)-5+6+789*A+B$	$B+A-9+8-7+6543-21$
6534	11128	$1-234-5-(-6789+A+B)$	$-B-A+9+8+7+6543-2*-1$
6535	11129	$-1*(-2-(-345+6789)-AB)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6543-21$
6536	11130	$1+2-(345-6789-AB)$	$-B-A+9+8-7+6543+2*1$
6537	11131	$-12-3+4*5+(-6-7)*8*(-9A+B)$	$-BA-(-98+7)-(-6543-21)$
6538	11132	$1*(2-3*4*-5-678-9A)*-B$	$B*(A-98+765-4+32-1)$
6539	11133	$1-2-3+4*(5-6)+789*A+B$	$BA-98-7+6543-21$
653A	11134	$1-2*-34-56-789*-A-B$	$-BA+9+87+6543+21$
653B	11135	$1+23-4-5*6+789*A+B$	$-B-A-9+8-7-(-6543-21)$
6540	11136	$-1-234+5+6789-A-B$	$B+A+9*876-54+(-3+2)*-1$
6541	11137	$-12-3-4-56-78*(9-AB)$	$-B+A-(-9-8-7-6543)-21$
6542	11138	$1-(234-5-(6789-A))-B$	$B+A+9-8*7+6543+21$
6543	11139	$12-345-6*(-7-8)*(9A+B)$	$-B+A-9-(8+7-(6543+21))$
6544	11140	$1-234-5-678*(9-A-B)$	$-B-A-9+8*7+6543-21$
6545	11141	$12-(345-6789-AB)$	$B+A-9+8+7-(-6543+21)$
6546	11142	$1-2-34+567+8*9A*B$	$B+A+9+8-7*6^5+4^4(3^2-1)$
6547	11143	$-1+2-3*45*-67+8-9AB$	$-B+A-9+8+7-(-6543-(-2+1))$
6548	11144	$1+23-4*-567-8*-9*A*B$	$BA-9-87+6543-21$
6549	11145	$-12-(-3-4-5)-(-6-789*A-B)$	$-BA+98+7-(-6543-21)$
654A	11146	$-1-234-5+6789A-B$	$-B+A-9+8+7+6543+2*1$
654B	11147	$-123-(45-6789-A*-B)$	$BA-98+7+6543-21$
6550	11148	$-1-234-56-7+89*-A*-B$	$-B+A-(-9+8-(7+6543))+2*1$
6551	11149	$1-2+34*-5+6789-AB$	$B-A+9+87-(-6543-21)$
6552	11150	$1-234+5+678*(-9A+B)$	$-B-(-A-9-8)-(7-6543+2*-1)$
6553	11151	$-1*-23*(456+7-89-AB)$	$B+A+9-(87-6543)-21$
6554	11152	$1-23*(45+6)*-7-(8-(9A+B))$	$-B+A+9-(87-6543)+2*-1$
6555	11153	$1-23-4-(-567+8*-9A*B)$	$B-A+(9+8)*(-76+543-21)$
6556	11154	$12+3-(4*-56-(-78+9)*-AB)$	$B+A-9-(-8+7)+6543-2*-1$
6557	11155	$12-3+4+5-6+789*A+B$	$-B+A-(9-(8-7+6543))+21$
6558	11156	$-1-234+5+6789A-B$	$-B+A+9-(87-6543)-2*-1$
6559	11157	$-1-234+5-6789*(A-B)$	$BA-98-7+6543-(2-1)$
655A	11158	$12-345+67+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+9*(-8*-7/-6+5^4+3)*2+1$
655B	11159	$1-2+34-5+6-(-789*A+B)$	$BA-(98+7)-(-6543-(2-1))$
6560	11160	$1-(234-5)-(-6789A-B)$	$-BA+9-87+65*4*(32-1)$
6561	11161	$-1+2+(-3-(45+6))*(-7-8)*(-9A+B)$	$BA-(98+7-6543-2-1)$
6562	11162	$1-234+56+7-8*-9AB$	$-BA+9+87*(65-(-43+2))-1$
6563	11163	$1-234-5-(-67+8*-9AB)$	$-B+A+9-(-8-7-6543)-(-2+1)$
6564	11164	$12-34*5+6789-AB$	$B-A-(-9-8)+7-6543*(-2+1)$
6565	11165	$1234-5-6*(-78-9AB)$	$-B+A+9+8+7+6543+2+1$
6566	11166	$12+3*(-4-5-67)+8*9AB$	$B-A-9*-876+5+4-(-3+21)$
6567	11167	$12-34*5*6+(-789-A)*-B$	$B+A+9-8-(-7-6543)-(2-1)$
6568	11168	$-1-(234+5-(6789-(-A-B)))$	$BA-9-87+6543-2+1$
6569	11169	$1-(2-34-5-6-789*A+B)$	$B+A+9-8+7-(-6543-2+1)$
656A	11170	$-123-4-(5-6789)-AB$	$BA-9-(87-6543)-(-2+1)$
656B	11171	$-1-2-3-45+6+78*(-9A+B)$	$BA-98+7-(-6543+2-1)$
6570	11172	$-1*2*(-3-4)*(-5+6*(7+89)+AB)$	$-B-A+9*8+7+6543-21$
6571	11173	$1-(2+34*5+6*7)-8*-9AB$	$B+A+9-(87-6543)-(2+1)$
6572	11174	$-1-23-4+5*-6*7+8*9AB$	$BA-98+7-(-6543+2*-1)$
6573	11175	$-123+4+5-67-8*-9AB$	$BA-98+7+6543+2+1$
6574	11176	$1*-2-3-4-(-56-789*A)-B$	$-B+A+9+8*-7+6543-21$
6575	11177	$-12+3+45-6+789*A+B$	$B-(-A+9+87-6543-2+1)$
6576	11178	$-1-(234-5-(6789+A)-B)$	$B-(-A+9+87-(6543-2*-1))$
6577	11179	$1*-234+5+6789-(-A-B)$	$-B+A+9-87+6543+21$
6578	11180	$-123-4-(-5-6789)-AB$	$-BA-98+(-7-65*4)*-32*-1$
6579	11181	$-1+2+3-45+6-78*(9-AB)$	$-B+A+98*7+(-6+5)*-4*-3*-21$
657A	11182	$-123-(4+56-7)+8*9AB$	$-B-A+9*876+54-32-1$
657B	11183	$-1+2+3-4-(-567+8*-9A*B)$	$BA-98-7-(-6543-21)$
6580	11184	$1*-2*-3*4*(-5-(678-9AB))$	$B-A+9*876+5+4-(3+2)+1$
6581	11185	$-1-(-23-4*-5)-((-6-789)*A+B)$	$-B+A+98*76+543-21$
6582	11186	$-1*-2*(3+4)*-567*(-8+9)*(A-B)$	$BA+9-(87-6543+2-1)$
6583	11187	$1-23*(4+5)+6+7-8*-9AB$	$-B-A-9+87-(-6543+21)$
6584	11188	$-123-(-4-5)-(-6789+AB)$	$BA-(-9+87-6543-2+1)$
6585	11189	$1+2-(3-4)-(-56-789*A+B)$	$B-A+9+8-(-7-6543-21)$
6586	11190	$123-4+5678+9AB$	$B-A-9-8*-7+6543+2+1$
6587	11191	$-123-4-5-(-6789A*B)$	$BA-98*-76-5+432*1$
6588	11192	$-1+23-(-45+6)+789*A-B$	$B-A-9*-876+5+4+3+2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6589	11193	$-12-345-67*(-8-(9+AB))$	$B-(-A-9)-(8-7)-(-6543-21)$
658A	11194	$1-(-2+3*45)+6789-AB$	$BA-9-(87-6543-21)$
658B	11195	$-1-2+34-56-78*(9-AB)$	$-B-A+9*876-5+4+32+1$
6590	11196	$-12+345+(678+9A)*B$	$-B+A-(9-876*(5+4))-(-3-21)$
6591	11197	$1+234-5+6+78*9A+B$	$BA-98-(-7-6543-21)$
6592	11198	$123+4+5678+9AB$	$B*(A9-8-(-7-654)-32)*1$
6593	11199	$1-(23-45*(6+7))+89*-A*-B$	$-B-A*(98-765-4*32)*1$
6594	11200	$-12*(-345-67-89-AB)$	$-B+A9-8*7+6543-2+1$
6595	11201	$1+23*(-4-5-(6-7))-8*-9AB$	$B+A9-(87-6543)+21$
6596	11202	$-1-2+3*4*5*6-78*-9A-B$	$-B-A+98-7+6543-21$
6597	11203	$1+2-3-4+56-789*-A+B$	$BA+9*-8-7+6543+2-1$
6598	11204	$12+3+4+567-8*-9A*B$	$BA-9*8-(7-6543)+2*1$
6599	11205	$1+23-45+6+78*(-9+AB)$	$BA-9*8-7+6543-(-2-1)$
659A	11206	$12+3+4+56+789*A-B$	$-B+A9-8*(-7-(-6-54))*(-3-21)$
659B	11207	$1-(-23+4)-(-567+8*9A*-B)$	$-B+A-(98*-76-543+2)-1$
65A0	11208	$1-2*3+4*-5*-6*7*8-9AB$	$B+A+9*(876-5)-(-43-(2+1))$
65A1	11209	$-123-(-4-(5+6789))-A*-B$	$-B-(-A-98*76-543+2-1)$
65A2	11210	$1*2*(3456-78-(-9A-B))$	$B-A-(-9*876-5-43+21)$
65A3	11211	$-1+23-45*-6-78*-9A+B$	$-B-(A-(-9+87))-(-6543+2-1)$
65A4	11212	$-1+2*-3*-456+7*89*A+B$	$BA+9*(-8+765-(-4*32-1))$
65A5	11213	$1+234+5+6+(78-9)*AB$	$-B-(A+9-87-6543)-(-2+1)$
65A6	11214	$-12+3-45*6-7-89*-A*B$	$-B-A+9+87+6543-2*-1$
65A7	11215	$123-4*(567-89*A)*B$	$-BA9-8*7*65*4*3*2*-1$
65A8	11216	$1234+5*6-(78-9)*-A*B$	$B-A+9-(876*(-5-4)-3-21)$
65A9	11217	$1+23+4+56+789*A-B$	$-B+A9-8-7+6543-21$
65AA	11218	$-1+2*(34+5-6)-789*-A+B$	$-B+A+9*876+5-4*-3*(2+1)$
65AB	11219	$-123+45-(67+8*-9AB)$	$BA98-76-5432-1$
65B0	11220	$123-4-56+789*A-B$	$BA98-76+5432*-1$
65B1	11221	$-1+234+5678+9A*B$	$BA98-(76+5432-1)$
65B2	11222	$-1*(-234-(5678+9A*B))$	$-B-A*-9+8-(7-6543-2-1)$
65B3	11223	$1-(-234-5678)-9A*-B$	$-B+A+9-876*(-5-4)+32-1$
65B4	11224	$-123+45*(-6+78-(-9A-B))$	$B-A+98-7+6543-21$
65B5	11225	$12+34+5*6-789*-A+B$	$-B+A+9-(-87-(6543-21))$
65B6	11226	$-1-(-2-34)-(-56-789*A)-B$	$-B-(A-98-(-7+6543))+2-1$
65B7	11227	$-1-2+3+4+5+6+78*(-9+AB)$	$B-A+9+87-(-6543+21)$
65B8	11228	$-12*(-3-45-6*-78+9A*-B)$	$-BA9-8+7654+3*-21$
65B9	11229	$-1-(-23-(-4+56)+789*-A)+B$	$B+A-9+87+6543-21$
65BA	11230	$-1-2345-67+89AB$	$-B-A-(-98+7-(6543+2+1))$
65BB	11231	$1*-2345-(67-89AB)$	$B*(-A9+876-54-3-21)$
6600	11232	$1-(2345-(-67+89AB))$	$-BA9+8-7*65*4*3*2+1$
6601	11233	$-123-4-(-5+6+7)-8*-9AB$	$-B+A9+8-7+6543-21$
6602	11234	$-123-(45-6*7+8*-9AB)$	$BA+9*876-54+3-21$
6603	11235	$123+45*-6+7+89AB$	$-B+A-(9-87-6543-(2+1))$
6604	11236	$-123-45+6789-A-B$	$-B-(-A-98-7-6543)-21$
6605	11237	$12-3-(-456+78*(-9A-B))$	$B-A-9+87+6543+2+1$
6606	11238	$-1-(-234-56)+78*9A-B$	$B-A+98-(-7-6543+21)$
6607	11239	$-12-34*56-(-7+89A)*-B$	$B+A9-8-7-(-6543+21)$
6608	11240	$1-(-234-56)-(-78*9A+B)$	$-B-(A-98-7-6543+2-1)$
6609	11241	$1-2*-345-67*(-8+9-AB)$	$-B-A9-8-(7+65*4*(32-1))$
660A	11242	$1*-2*(-34+567-89A)*B$	$B*(A-98+765+4+32+1)$
660B	11243	$123-45+6+789*A-B$	$-B+A9-8-7+6543+2-1$
6610	11244	$-1*2*3*(-4*-56*7-(-89+AB))$	$-BA9+8+7654+3*-21$
6611	11245	$-1234-56-(-789A-B)$	$-B+A9-8-7-(-6543-2-1)$
6612	11246	$12+3+4-5+6-78*(9-AB)$	$BA-9-8-(-7-6543)-21$
6613	11247	$-123-45-(67-89*A*B)$	$B+A+9+87+6543-21$
6614	11248	$1+23*-4+5+6789-AB$	$-B-(-A-98+7-6543)+2-1$
6615	11249	$-1+2*(3-45)-(-6789+AB)$	$-B+A+9+87+6543-2+1$
6616	11250	$12+34-5+(-6-789)*-A+B$	$B-A+9-(-87-6543-2*-1)$
6617	11251	$-1+2*-34-5-67+8*9AB$	$-B-A9*-87-(-6*5-43)*-21$
6618	11252	$-1+2-3+45+(6+789)*A+B$	$-B-A+98-7+6543+21$
6619	11253	$-1-2-34*(5-(-6+7))+8*9AB$	$-B+A+9+87+6543+2+1$
661A	11254	$-1*-2*(3456-(78+9A)+B)$	$B+A9+(-8+7)*-6543-21$
661B	11255	$123-4-56*7-89*A*-B$	$-B-A-(-9-87-6543-21)$
6620	11256	$12*-3*(-45+6-78-9A-B)$	$BA-9-(8+7-6543+2-1)$
6621	11257	$1-23-(-45-6-78*(-9+AB))$	$B+A-(9-87)-(-6543-2-1)$
6622	11258	$1-23-45-67+8*9AB$	$BA-9-(8+7)+6543-(-2+1)$
6623	11259	$-123-4-(-5-6-7)-8*-9AB$	$-B-(-A9+8-7-6543)-(-2-1)$
6624	11260	$-1+234+56-78*-9A+B$	$B-A+98-(-7-6543+2+1)$
6625	11261	$1+2*(-34-5)+6789-AB$	$-B+A9+8-7+6543+2+1$
6626	11262	$-1*(-2-34*-5-6789+A+B)$	$BA-9+8+7+6543-21$
6627	11263	$1+2-(-34+5*-6*(7+8+9A)*B)$	$B-(-A9+8+7)-(-6543-(-2+1))$
6628	11264	$1-2*34-56-7-8*-9AB$	$BA+9-8+7+6543-21$
6629	11265	$123-45+6-(789*-A-B)$	$-B-A98*-7-(65-(4+321))$
662A	11266	$-1*-2*(34-(-5+6)*78+9)*-AB$	$-B-(A-98-7-6543-21)$
662B	11267	$-1-234-(-5-6789)+A*B$	$-B+A9-8-(-7-(6543+21))$
6630	11268	$-1*(2345-6*-7-89AB)$	$BA-9-8+7+6543-2-1$
6631	11269	$-1-23-45+6789-AB$	$BA98-7*6-5432+1$
6632	11270	$1*-23-45-(-6789+AB)$	$BA-9+8-7+6543-2-1$
6633	11271	$-123-45+67+8*9AB$	$B+A-(-9-87-6543+2)+1$
6634	11272	$-1-2*(3-4*5*6-7*-8*9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A-98)-7-(-6543-21)$
6635	11273	$12-3+4+5+(-67-8*9A)*-B$	$B+A+9+87+6543+2-1$
6636	11274	$1-2+3+4+5+6-78*(9-AB)$	$B-A+98-7+6543+21$
6637	11275	$-1+23-4-(-5-6)*7(78-9A)*B$	$-BA9-8-(-7654-(-3-21))$
6638	11276	$-12-3*-4*-5+6789-AB$	$BA-9+8-7-(-6543-2-1)$
6639	11277	$-1-2-34*5+6789+A-B$	$B+A9-8+7+6543-2+1$
663A	11278	$-1-234-(5-6789)+AB$	$BA+9-8-7+6543+2+1$
663B	11279	$-1-2*(3+4+5+6)+89*A*B$	$B-(-A9+8)-(-7-6543)-(-2+1)$
6640	11280	$-12-3-45+6789-AB$	$-BA9+8+7654-32-1$
6641	11281	$-1+2-34*5-(-6789-A+B)$	$-BA9+8+7654+32*-1$
6642	11282	$-1+2-3-45-67-8*-9AB$	$-BA9+8+7654-32+1$
6643	11283	$1+234*-5*-6-(-7-(8+9AB))$	$-B+A9+8-7+6543+21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6644	11284	$1*2*(-3-45-6)*(-7-89+A+B)$	$B+A+98+7-(6543-2+1)$
6645	11285	$-1-23*(45+678-9AB)$	$BA-9+8+7+6543+2*-1$
6646	11286	$-1*23*(45-(-678+9AB))$	$B+A-(-98-7)+6543+2+1$
6647	11287	$-12-3*45+6789-A-B$	$BA+9-8+7+6543-2*1$
6648	11288	$12+3+45-6-78*(9-AB)$	$-B+A987-(6+5+4321)$
6649	11289	$-12+3*-45*-6+(-7+8*-9)*-AB$	$B-(-A9+8+7)-(-6543-21)$
664A	11290	$1-234+5-(-6789-AB)$	$BA+9+8-7+6543-2+1$
664B	11291	$-12-34-5+6789-AB$	$B-(-A987+6*5+4321)$
6650	11292	$1-2*3-(45-6789)-AB$	$BA-(-9+8-7-6543-2-1)$
6651	11293	$1-2-(3+45-(6789-AB))$	$B-A*-9+8*7+6543-2-1$
6652	11294	$-12+345-67*(-8-9A-B)$	$-BA9-8+7654-3*(2+1)$
6653	11295	$123+4*(-56-7)+8*9AB$	$B+A9+8-(-7-6543-2)-1$
6654	11296	$-1-(2345+6+7-89AB)$	$B-A9*-87+65*(-43+21)$
6655	11297	$-123+45-(-6+7)+8*9AB$	$-BA9-8+7654-3-2-1$
6656	11298	$-12*3*(-45-67-8-(9A+B))$	$B-(-A-9*(876-54+3*21))$
6657	11299	$1+2+(3+4-5+6)*(-7-8+9AB)$	$-BA9-8+7654-3-2+1$
6658	11300	$-123-4-5-(-6789-A+B)$	$-B+A987+6-(5+4321)$
6659	11301	$-1+2+3-(45-6789)-AB$	$-BA9-8+7654-3+2-1$
665A	11302	$-123-4-(5-6789+A-B)$	$BA-(-9-8-(7+6543-2-1))$
665B	11303	$-1*(2+3+4+5-6789+AB)$	$B-(-A9+8)-(-7-6543-21)$
6660	11304	$1-234*-5*6+(7+8+9A)*B$	$BA+9+8+7+6543-(2-1)$
6661	11305	$1-2*(3-(-4-5))*(678-9AB)$	$-BA9-8-(-7654-3+2)+1$
6662	11306	$12-(34+5+6+7-8*9AB)$	$BA98-7+6*543*2+1$
6663	11307	$-12+3-4+5+6789-A*B$	$BA+9*876-5+4*(-3-(-2+1))$
6664	11308	$-123+4-5+6789+A-B$	$-BA9-8+7654+3+2*1$
6665	11309	$-1*(2345-6-(-7+89AB))$	$-BA9-8+7654+3+2+1$
6666	11310	$-1234+5+6+789A-B$	$BA98+7-6-5432-1$
6667	11311	$-123+4*-5+6789+A+B$	$BA98-(-7+6-5432*-1)$
6668	11312	$-123-4-(-5-6789)-A+B$	$-BA9-8+7654+3*(2+1)$
6669	11313	$-123-45-(6+7+89*-A*B)$	$-BA9+8+7654-3-2-1$
666A	11314	$1-2-34-(-5-6789+AB)$	$BA+9-(8-7-6543-21)$
666B	11315	$-123-(4+5-67-8*9AB)$	$-BA9+8+7654-3-2+1$
6670	11316	$-1+2-34+5+6789-AB$	$BA-(-9-8)-(-7-6543-21)$
6671	11317	$-123-4*-56-78*(9-AB)$	$-BA9+8+7654-(3-2+1)$
6672	11318	$1-(-2+3)-(45-6789+A*B)$	$-BA9-(-8-(7654-3-2*-1))$
6673	11319	$12-34-5+6789-AB$	$BA98-(-7-6*-543*2*1)$
6674	11320	$-1234+5-6+789A+B$	$-BA9+8+7654+3+2*-1$
6675	11321	$-1-23+4-(5-6789+AB)$	$-BA9+8+7654-(-3+2)+1$
6676	11322	$-1-2345+6+7+89AB$	$B+A987+6-5-4321$
6677	11323	$-12+3*(456-7)-8*9*-AB$	$BA98+7+6+5432*-1$
6678	11324	$1-2345-(-6-7-89AB)$	$BA98-(-7-6)-(5432-1)$
6679	11325	$-1-(23+4+5+6-7-8*9AB)$	$-BA9+8+7654-3*-2*1$
667A	11326	$1+2+3*-45+6789-A+B$	$-BA9-(-8-7654-3*2)+1$
667B	11327	$12-34*-5-6+789*A-B$	$BA-9*-876+5-4+3*2*1$
6680	11328	$1-2-34+5+6*-7+8*9AB$	$BA+98*76+543-21$
6681	11329	$12-(34-5)-(-6789+AB)$	$-B+A987+6*5-4321$
6682	11330	$-123+4-5+6789+A+B$	$BA+9+8+7+6543+21$
6683	11331	$-1-(23-4-5-(6789-AB))$	$-BA9-8-(-7654-3-21)$
6684	11332	$-1234+5+6+789A+B$	$B+A987+6+5-4321$
6685	11333	$1-23+4+5-(-6789+AB)$	$BA-9*-876-5-(4+3-21)$
6686	11334	$-12-3-4+5+6789-AB$	$BA98-(76+5*-4*-321)$
6687	11335	$1-2+345-(-6+78*-9A+B)$	$-B-(-A9-87-6543)-21$
6688	11336	$-1-(2-3-4+5+6+7-8*9AB)$	$B+A+9+8*7+6*5^4*3^4(2-1)$
6689	11337	$-1+2-3*45+67+8*9AB$	$B+A+9+8*7+6*5^4*3+2-1$
668A	11338	$-123-(-456+78*-9A)+B$	$-B+A9-8*-7+6543+21$
668B	11339	$-123-(45-6)-(-7+89*A*-B)$	$B-A-9*-876-5*(-4-3-21)$
6690	11340	$-12+3-4+5+6789-AB$	$-BA9-(8-7654)-(-32+1)$
6691	11341	$1-(-2+3)-(4+5-6789+AB)$	$-BA9-(-8-7654)-3+21$
6692	11342	$-1-23+4-(5-6789-A*-B)$	$-BA9-8+7654-(-32-1)$
6693	11343	$-1-2-3+4-5-(-6789+AB)$	$BA+9+8*7+6543-2-1$
6694	11344	$1-(23-(4-5))-(-6789+A*B)$	$B+A*9-(-87-6543-2)-1$
6695	11345	$-1-2*(-3456+78)-(-9+AB)$	$BA+9+8*7+6543-2+1$
6696	11346	$1-2+3*(4-5)+6789-AB$	$BA+9*876+(-54+32)*-1$
6697	11347	$1-2-3-4+5+6789-AB$	$-BA9-(-8-7654-3)+21$
6698	11348	$-12+3-(-4-5-(6789-AB))$	$-B+A-9*(-876+5+4-(3+21))$
6699	11349	$1+2-3+4-5+6789-AB$	$BA-9*-876+5-(-4-3)+21$
669A	11350	$-1+234+5678+9AB$	$BA-9+87-(-6543+21)$
669B	11351	$12+34*-56-(-7+89A*-B)$	$BA-98*76-(-543+2*1)$
66A0	11352	$1+234+5678+9AB$	$B*A9*(87+6-54-(32-1))$
66A1	11353	$-1-(2-(-3-(-4-5-6789+AB)))$	$BA-9-8*-7+6543+21$
66A2	11354	$-1+23-(4+5)-(67-8*9AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7*6-5^4)-3*2^1$
66A3	11355	$-1234+56-(-789A+B)$	$-B-A-9*-8*(76-(-54-3-2+1))$
66A4	11356	$12+3-4-56-7+8*9AB$	$-BA9+8+7654+32-1$
66A5	11357	$-1+2-3+4+5+6789-AB$	$-BA9+8+7654-32*-1$
66A6	11358	$12-(-3+4-(-5-(-6789+AB)))$	$-BA9+8-(-7654-32-1)$
66A7	11359	$1+2-3+4-(-5-6789)-AB$	$-B+A9-(-87-6543+2-1)$
66A8	11360	$12-3+4-5+6789-AB$	$BA*(-98-(-7+6)-(-54*-3-(2+1)))$
66A9	11361	$-1+2*-3*(-4-5)*(6-7)-8*-9AB$	$-B+A9-(-87-6543)-(-2+1)$
66AA	11362	$-123+45+6789+A-B$	$BA+9*876+54+3-21$
66AB	11363	$1+2-(-3-45)*(6-7)+8*9AB$	$-B+A9+87+6543+2+1$
66B0	11364	$-123-(-45-6789)-(-A-B)$	$B-A98*-7*(6-5)+4+321$
66B1	11365	$1+2-(-3-(4+5+6789)+AB)$	$BA+98-7+6543-21$
66B2	11366	$1-(2+3-4)-(-5-6789-A*-B)$	$BA-9*-876-(-5-4-(32-1))$
66B3	11367	$12+3-(-4+5)*-6789-AB$	$BA+9*(876+5)-(-4-3-2-1)$
66B4	11368	$12+3-(-4-5-(6789-AB))$	$-BA9+8765-4*321$
66B5	11369	$1+23-(-4+5)-(-6789+AB)$	$-B-A98-7*-65*4*3*2*1$
66B6	11370	$-1+2*(-345-6)+(-789-A)*-B$	$B+A+9+(-8-7)*-6*(5^4(4-(3-2)))+1$
66B7	11371	$1-234*-5*(67+8*-9)+A*-B$	$BA-9*-8-(-7-6543)+21$
66B8	11372	$12-3-(-4+56)-(-7-8*9AB)$	$BA-9+87+6543-2-1$
66B9	11373	$-12-3+45-67-8*-9AB$	$BA-9*-876-(-5-(43-2))-1$
66BA	11374	$-1-(-2-3-4+5-6789)+A*-B$	$B*(-A9-8-7-654+32)*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
66BB	11375	-1-23+45+6789-AB	-B-A98*7-6543*2*-1
6700	11376	-1*(23-(45+6789-AB))	-B+A987+65-4321
6701	11377	1-23+45+6789-AB	BA-9-(87+6543+2)*-1
6702	11378	1-2-(-3+45-(6+7+8*9AB))	BA-9+87+6543+2+1
6703	11379	-12+3+45-(67-8*9AB)	B-(-A9-(87+6543-2))-1
6704	11380	-1+2+3-45+6+7-8*-9AB	-B-A9+(8+7-6)*(5-43*-21)
6705	11381	-12+3+45+6789-AB	B+A9+87+6543-(2-1)
6706	11382	-1-(2-3+45)-(-6789+AB)	-B-A98+7654+3*21
6707	11383	1-23+4*5+6+7+8*9AB	B-A9*(-8-76)+5+43*-21
6708	11384	1-2-(-3+45)-(-6789+AB)	B+A-9*(-8*-7/-6-5^4+3)*2-1
6709	11385	-1+23+4+5+6789-AB	-B+A9+87+6543+21
670A	11386	1-(2+3-45+67-8*9AB)	-B-A*(-98-765)-432+1
670B	11387	12+3+4-(5-6789)+A*-B	BA+98-7-(6543+2)-1
6710	11388	-1-2345-(-67-89AB)	BA+98-7+6543-2*1
6711	11389	-1*(2345-67-89AB)	BA-98*-7*6+5*43*21
6712	11390	1-2345+67+89AB	BA+9-(-87-6543+2+1)
6713	11391	-12+3+4-5-6-7+8*9AB	BA+98-7-(-6543-2+1)
6714	11392	-12+3+45+6789-AB	BA+98-(7-6543-2*1)
6715	11393	-1*(2-34-5-(6789-AB))	BA-(-98+7-6543-2)+1
6716	11394	1-2+3+4+5+6789-AB	BA+9-(-87-6543)-(-2+1)
6717	11395	-1*(-23+45-67)*(89-A*-B)	BA+9+87+(-6543-2)*-1
6718	11396	-1+2+3+4+5+6789-AB	BA-(-9-87-6543)-(-2-1)
6719	11397	12-(-34+56)-7+8*9AB	B-A98*7+6543*2*1
671A	11398	-1+23-4+5+6789+A*-B	B-(-A987-65)-4321
671B	11399	12-(-34+5-6789+AB)	BA98+76-(5432+1)
6720	11400	-1*(23-(-45+6789+A-B))	BA98+76+5432*-1
6721	11401	-1-23-45+6789-A+B	BA98+76-(5432-1)
6722	11402	-12+3+4+5-(-6789-A*-B)	BA+98+7+6543+2*-1
6723	11403	1-23-45+6789-A+B	BA-(-98-7)-(-6543+2-1)
6724	11404	1234-5-67+8*-9*-AB	B-A98+7654-3*21
6725	11405	1-(2-3-45)-(-6789+AB)	BA+98+7+6543+2-1
6726	11406	-12+3*4+5-6-7+8*9AB	BA+98+7+6543+2*1
6727	11407	-12-(3-45)+6789-A*B	B+A9+87+6543+21
6728	11408	1-2-3+4+5-(6+7)-8*-9AB	B+A-((-9*(-8*(-7+6)+5^4)+3)*2+1)
6729	11409	1-(-2-3-45-6789+AB)	-B+A*9-87*(-6+54-3)*2*-1
672A	11410	-12-3-45+6789+A-B	BA+9*(-876-5-4-3+2)*-1
672B	11411	1-2+34*5+6789+AB	BA98-7-6+5*4*-321
6730	11412	-1-2*-3-(45-6789+A+B)	B+A+(-9-(-8*7-6*5^4))*3^A(2-1)
6731	11413	1+2-(-3+45-6789-(-A-B))	-B-A+9*876+54*(3+2-1)
6732	11414	1234+5-67+8*9*AB	-BA-9*(-876-54-(3-21))
6733	11415	12+3*4*(5-678)*(9-A)-B	BA+98-7+6543+21
6734	11416	-1+2-34-5+6789-(A+B)	B+A+9*(-8+7+6+5^4+3)*2+1
6735	11417	-1+2+3+4+5+6789+A*-B	BA+9*876-5+43*2*-1
6736	11418	-12-(-3+45)-(-6789+A)+B	BA+9+87-(-6543-21)
6737	11419	-123+4-5+6789-A*-B	-B-A98+7654+32*-1
6738	11420	-1+23-4-5-6-7+8*9AB	-B-(A98-7654+32)+1
6739	11421	-123-4+5+6789-A*-B	BA98+7+6*(54-3)*-21
673A	11422	-1+2*34-56-7-8*-9AB	BA-9*-876+54+32*1
673B	11423	1-2-3-45+6789+A-B	B+A-9*(8-(7+(-6-5^4-3)*2))-1
6740	11424	12+3-45+6789-A-B	B+A-9*((-8*7+6)*5^4-3^A(2+1))
6741	11425	-1-(-2+3-(-45+6789)-A+B)	BA98-(-7+6)+5*-4*321
6742	11426	-1+2-(34-5-6789+A)-B	B+A9*(8+7+65)+4-321
6743	11427	-1+2-34-5-67+89*A*B	B+A*9*87+(-6+54)*(32-1)
6744	11428	1+2-3+(45-6789)*(A-B)	-B+A9*87+65*-4*3*2*1
6745	11429	-1-2-(-3+45)-(-6789+A-B)	-B-A98-(-7654+3)-21
6746	11430	12+3+4+5+6789-A*B	B+A-9*(-8*7-6/5^4+3)/(2+1)
6747	11431	1+23+45+6789-AB	B+A+(9*(8+7)*6+5)^*(4*3+2^A)
6748	11432	12-3+(-45+6)*(-7-(89+AB))	B-(-A+9*(-876-54+32))-1
6749	11433	1+2+3-(45-6789-A)-B	-BA98+7-(6+54)*-321
674A	11434	-1-2-34-5+6789-A+B	BA+9*(87-6*-54*3)-2-1
674B	11435	1+2+3-45-(-6789+A)+B	-B-A98-(-7654+3+21)
6750	11436	-1+23*(45+6)+78*(9A-B)	B+A+(9/-8+7)*6^5/4-3*2/1
6751	11437	1+2*-3-45+67-8*-9AB	BA98-(-7-6)+5*4*-321
6752	11438	-12+3-(45-6789)-(-A-B)	B+A+(9/-8+7)*6^5/4-(3+2-1)
6753	11439	-12-3*45-(-6789-AB)	B+A+9*(-8*-7-(6^5+4)/3)/-2*1
6754	11440	-123+4-5+6789+AB	B*(A9-8-(7-654-(-3+2)+1))
6755	11441	-1+23-(-4+5)-(6-7)*8*9AB	B+A98*7-(-65-4-321)
6756	11442	-123-(4-5-6789-AB)	-BA-98+76*5*(43-21)
6757	11443	12-3*45+6789A-B	B+A+(9/-8+7)*6^5/4+3-2*1
6758	11444	-1+2+3+4*-5+6789-A-B	B+A+(9/-8+7)*6^5/4+3-(2-1)
6759	11445	-1-2*-3+4*5+6789-A-B	B+A+(9+8)*(7*6+5^4+3+2)^A1
675A	11446	1-(2-(-34+5+6789-A)))+B	-BA-98-7*(6+5)*4*32*-1
675B	11447	1-23-4-(5-6789+A)-B	B+A+(9/-8+7)*6^5/4+3+2*1
6760	11448	1*-2-(34-(-5+67))+8*9AB	-B-A-987*-6-5*(-432-1)
6761	11449	-1-2*(3-45)-(-6789+AB)	B+A-9*(-8-(-7/6+5^4+3))*2+1
6762	11450	-123+4+5+6789+AB	B-A98+765*4*3-21
6763	11451	-1+23-(-4-5)-(6-7)*-8*-9AB	B-(A98-7654+3)-21
6764	11452	-1-23+4-5-6789*(A-B)	-B-A98+7654-3-2*1
6765	11453	-1-(-23-45)-(-6*-7-8*9AB)	-B-A98-765*4*3*(-2+1)
6766	11454	-1-2-34-(5-6789)-(-A-B)	-B-A98+7654+3*(-2+1)
6767	11455	-1-23-4+5+6789-A+B	-B-A98-(-7654+3)-(-2+1)
6768	11456	1+2+3*-45+6789+AB	-B+A+9*(876+5+43-21)
6769	11457	123-4+5+6789*(9-AB)	-B+A98*7+6*(-5-43*-2-1)
676A	11458	-1-2*-34+5-6*7-8*-9AB	-B-A98+7654+3-2*1
676B	11459	12-34-(-5-6789-A)-B	-B-A98+7654+3-(2-1)
6770	11460	-1+234*5+(-67+89A)*B	-B-A98+7654+3*(2-1)
6771	11461	-12+3-4+5-67-89*A*-B	-B-A98+7654+3+2-1
6772	11462	1*-23+4+5+6789+A-B	-B+A*(9-(8-765))+432-1
6773	11463	1234+5678+9*(-A-B)	-B-A98+7654-3*2*-1
6774	11464	12-34-5-(-67-8*9AB)	-B-A98+7654+3*2+1
6775	11465	-1-23-4-5+6789-(-A-B)	BA-9-8-7*-6*5*(43+2+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6776	11466	$1-2-3+45-6-(-7-8^*9AB)$	$BA98+7^*6-5^*-4^*-321$
6777	11467	$12-3^*45-(-6789-AB)$	$-BA+9-87-65^*-4^*32-1$
6778	11468	$123-(45-6789+AB)$	$B+A+(9^*-8+7-6^*5^4)^*-3+2^*1$
6779	11469	$-1-2+3-(-4-5-(6789-A-B))$	$-BA+9-87+65^*4^*32+1$
677A	11470	$12-(3-(4-5+6789-A-B))$	$-B-A^*(-9-(8+765))(-(-4-321))$
677B	11471	$12-34-5-(-6789-(A+B))$	$BA9+87^*6+5^*4^*321$
6780	11472	$1+2-3-4-(-5+67)+89^*A^*B$	$BA9-87^*-65-4^*-321$
6781	11473	$-12-3-(-4-5)-6789^*(A-B)$	$B-A98+7654-3-2-1$
6782	11474	$-1-2-3-(-4-(-5+6789))(-(-A+B))$	$BA98+76^*(-54-(32-1))$
6783	11475	$-1-(-23+45-(6789+A+B))$	$B-A98+7654-(3+2)+1$
6784	11476	$-1-2-3+4^*-5+6789+A+B$	$B-A98+7654-3^*(2-1)$
6785	11477	$-1+23-(4-(-5+6789-(A+B)))$	$B-A98+7654-3+2-1$
6786	11478	$12-(-3+4)-(-5-6789)-(A+B)$	$B-(A98-7654)-(-3+2^*-1)$
6787	11479	$1+2-3+4+56-7-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A98+7654-3+2+1$
6788	11480	$-12^*(-3+4-5-6789+AB)$	$B-A98+7654+3+2^*-1$
6789	11481	$-12-(-34+5)+6789-(A+B)$	$B-A98+7654+3-2+1$
678A	11482	$1+2-(-34-5^*6)-(-7+8^*-9AB)$	$-B-A-9-8^*(7+(6+(-5-4)^3))^*2^1$
678B	11483	$-1-2-3+4+5+6789+A-B$	$B-(A98-(7654+3+2)+1)$
6790	11484	$-12-3+4-5+6789+A+B$	$B-(A98-7654-3)+2^*1$
6791	11485	$-1-2^*-3+4^*5+6789-(A+B)$	$-B-A98+7654+3+2+1$
6792	11486	$-12-3-4+5-(-6789-A)+B$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+6+(-5-4)^3)/2^1-1$
6793	11487	$1-(2+3-4-(5+6789-A+B))$	$B+A+9^*(876-5-4^*-3+2+1)$
6794	11488	$1^*-2345-6-7^*-89^*(A+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8-(7-6+5^4+3))^*2+1$
6795	11489	$123-(45-6789)-A^*B$	$B-A98-7^*(654+3)^*2^*-1$
6796	11490	$-1+2^*3^*4^*5+6789-A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7/6-(5^4+3))/2^1-1$
6797	11491	$-1-2-(-3-4-5)-(-6789+A)+B$	$-B-A+9^*(-8+(7-(6-5))^4-3^2)+1$
6798	11492	$-1-(2-(34-5)-6789-(-A-B))$	$-BA-9^*-876-5-(-4-321)$
6799	11493	$1+2+3+456-78^*-9A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7-6^*(5^4+3)))/(2+1)$
679A	11494	$-123+45+6789+AB$	$-B-A98+7654+32-1$
679B	11495	$-1+2-(-3-4^*5+67-89^*A^*B)$	$-B^*(A+9)^*(-8-7+6^*-5-(4^*3-2^*1))$
67A0	11496	$12+3+4-(-56+7+8^*-9AB)$	$-B-A98+7654+32+1$
67A1	11497	$1-2-3+4-5-(-6789-(A+B))$	$-BA-9+8^*-7+65^*4^*32^*1$
67A2	11498	$1+23-(-4+5)-67+89^*-A^*-B$	$B+A+9^*-8^*(-7/-6-5/4^3)/2-1$
67A3	11499	$1-(-23+4+5)-(-6789-A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8^*7^*(6+5+4))^*3^*2^1$
67A4	11500	$12+3-(4-5-6789+A)+B$	$-B-(A+9^*(8-765)+4^*-321)$
67A5	11501	$-1-2-(-3-4+5-6789-A)+B$	$B-A98+7654-3+2+1$
67A6	11502	$12-3+4+5+6789-A+B$	$-BA^*(9-(8-7)-65-4^*3+2^*1)$
67A7	11503	$-12+34-56-7+89^*A^*B$	$-BA+9^*8^*7+6543+2^*1$
67A8	11504	$1-(-2-(-3-(-4-5)+67)+8^*-9AB)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7+6-5^*-4^3)/2-1$
67A9	11505	$-1+2+3+4-5+6789+A+B$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7^*6^*5/4^3+2)^1$
67AA	11506	$-1-2-3^*-4-5+6789+A+B$	$B+A98^*7-6+(5-432)^*-1$
67AB	11507	$-1-23-(-45-6789)-(A-B)$	$B-A98+7654-(-3-21)$
67B0	11508	$1^*-2^*(3+4)^*(5-6789+9A+B)$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-(-6^*(5+4/3))^2)^1$
67B1	11509	$1-(-23-4+5-6789+A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(8+7)-6^5/-4^*3^2+1$
67B2	11510	$1-(-2-3)-(-4-5-67)-8^*-9AB$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*(6^*(5+4^*3))^*2+1$
67B3	11511	$12+3+4-(-5-67+8^*-9AB)$	$B+A-9+87+65^*-4^*(-32+1)$
67B4	11512	$1234+5678-(9+AB)$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(-7+6-(-5-4)^3)/2-1$
67B5	11513	$12+3-4-(-5-67)+8^*9AB$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(-7^*-6+5^4+3^2)^1$
67B6	11514	$1+234-(-56+789^*-A+B)$	$-BA+9-(8^*7-65^*-4^*-32+1)$
67B7	11515	$1+23+456-78^*-9A-B$	$-BA+9+(87+6-5)^*4^*(3+2+1)$
67B8	11516	$-12-(3-45)-(-6789-A+B)$	$B-(A98-7654-32+1)$
67B9	11517	$-1-2+3+4+5-6^*7+89^*A^*B$	$B-A98-(-7654-32)^*1$
67BA	11518	$12-(-3-4+5-6789-A)+B$	$B-A98+7654+32+1$
67BB	11519	$12+3-4^*-5-(-6789+A)+B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)^*7+(6^5-4)^*-3/-2+1$
6800	11520	$123+4-5+6789-AB$	$-B^*-A+(9^*(8+7)^*6+5)^*(4^*3+2^1)$
6801	11521	$-12-(3-(-45-(-6789+A^*-B)))$	$-B-A-9+8^*(7+6^*5+4-3)^2-1$
6802	11522	$-12-(-3-45-6789-A+B)$	$B+A+9+(8-7^*6)^*(5-(4+3)^2+1)$
6803	11523	$-12+34-5+6789+A+B$	$-BA+9^*(8+765)+4^*321$
6804	11524	$-12+3+4+5+6789-(A-B)$	$-B-A9^*8-(-7654+321)$
6805	11525	$1-2+3+4+5-6789^*(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7)^*-6^*(-5+4^3)/2-1$
6806	11526	$-1234-567^*(-8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A98^*7+6^*5-(-432-1)$
6807	11527	$-1+23+4-5-(-6789-A-B)$	$B-A98^*7+6-(-5-432+1)$
6808	11528	$-1+2-(-34-(5+6789))-(-A-B)$	$-B-A-9+8+(76+54)^*3^*2+1$
6809	11529	$1-23-(-45-6789-A)+B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7)^*(-6^*-5^*4^3-2)/1$
680A	11530	$1234+5678+9-AB$	$-B-A-9-8^*(7+6-(5+4)^3)^2+1$
680B	11531	$-1-(-2+3-(45+6789))-A+B$	$B-A^*-9^*8^*(7-6-5)^*-4-3+2+1$
6810	11532	$1^*-23-45+6789+AB$	$-B-(A98-7654-3^*21)$
6811	11533	$1-23-45+6789+AB$	$B+A+9^*(-8+(7-(6-5))^4-3^2)+1$
6812	11534	$-1+23+4+5-6789^*-A+B$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+(6-(5+4)^3))^*2+1$
6813	11535	$-1^*(-2+3-(-45-6789))^*(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7^*6)^*(-5^*-4^*(3+2)+1)$
6814	11536	$1-2+34-(5-(6789-(-A-B)))$	$B+A^*(98+765-43)+2+1$
6815	11537	$1-(2-3)-(-45-6789+A-B)$	$-BA-9^*-87+6^*-54^*(-3-2+1)$
6816	11538	$-12-3-(-45-6789)-(-A-B)$	$-B-(A9+87-65^*-43^*(-2-1))$
6817	11539	$1-(-2-3-45)-(-6789-A+B)$	$B^*(-A9-(-876+54))-(-3+2)-1$
6818	11540	$1-2-(-3+45-6789+A^*-B)$	$B+A+98+7+65^*-4^*(-32+1)$
6819	11541	$1+23+4+5+6789-A-B$	$B+A+9^*(876-5-(-4-(32+1)))$
681A	11542	$1-2^*-3-(-45-6789)-A+B$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7-6)^*5^*4^3/2+1$
681B	11543	$-1+23-(-4-5^*-6-(-7-89^*A^*-B))$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+(6-(5+4)^3))^*2+1$
6820	11544	$12-3+4+5+6789+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7)^*-6^*-5/4^3-3+2+1$
6821	11545	$1234+5678-(9A-B)$	$B+A-9^*(8+7)+(-6^5+4)^*-3/2+1$
6822	11546	$-1-2^*(-3456+78)+9^*A-B$	$-BA+98^*(76-5)-4^*-321$
6823	11547	$123-45+6+7+8^*9AB$	$B+A+(-9+8+7)^*(-6^*-5^*4^3+2-1)$
6824	11548	$-12+3-45+6789+AB$	$-BA+9-8^*-7^*65+4321$
6825	11549	$-1-2-3+4+5+6789+A+B$	$B+A-9^*(8+7)-6^5/-4^*3^2-1$
6826	11550	$-12^*-3^*(-45^*(-6-7+8))-(-9+A)+B$	$-B^*(-A9-8-(7-(654-3)-21))$
6827	11551	$123+4-(-5-6789)+A^*-B$	$B-A-9^*(8+7)-6^5/-4^*3^2+1$
6828	11552	$12+3+4+5+6789-(A-B)$	$B+A+9-8-(-76-54)^*3^*2+1$
6829	11553	$-1-2-3-45-(-6789-AB)$	$-BA-9+8-7+65^*4^*32-1$
682A	11554	$123+4+5-(-6^*-7+8^*-9AB)$	$B-(A98-7654-3^*21)$
682B	11555	$1+2-3+4+5+6789+A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7-6^5/-4^*3))^*2^*1$
6830	11556	$-1^*-2^*(3456+78-9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7-6^5/-4^*3))^*2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6831	11557	-1-(-2+3)-45+6789+AB	-BA-9*-876-(-54-321)
6832	11558	1-2-3-4+5+(6-7+89*-A)*-B	B+A+(9/(8-(7-6*(5+4))^3+2))^3-1
6833	11559	-1-2+3-45+6789+AB	B-A-9*-876+5*(43+21)
6834	11560	12-34-5+6789-A*-B	-B+A-9*-876-54*3*-2-1
6835	11561	1-(-23-(45+6789))-A+B	B*(-A-(9-87-654-32-1))
6836	11562	1234-(5-67+8*9*-AB)	-B-A+9+(-8-7+6^5/4)*-3*-2/1
6837	11563	-12-34+5+6789+AB	-B-A+9+(87-6*-5*-4*-3)*21
6838	11564	-1-2-34-5+6789+AB	BA98-76*5*4*(-3-2)*-1
6839	11565	12+3-(-45-67-8*9AB)	BA+9*876-5*(43-2)*-1
683A	11566	12-3-(-45-6789)+A+B	B+A+9+87*(65-4+32+1)
683B	11567	-1+2*3*4*(-567+89A+B)	-B+A98+(-7-6)*543-2+1
6840	11568	-1*2*-3*-4*(567-89A-B)	-BA-9+8+7+65*-4*-32*1
6841	11569	1*2-34-5+6789+AB	-B-A*(-98-765+4+32+1)
6842	11570	1+2-34-5-(-6789-AB)	B+A+9*-8+(-7+6^5/4)*3*2-1
6843	11571	1234+56+7-8*9*-AB	BA98+7+6*-5*-4*3*-21
6844	11572	12+3-(-45-6789-(A+B))	-BA+9+8-7+65*4*32*1
6845	11573	-123-45*6*7-89A*-B	BA-9*-876-5*-43-2*1
6846	11574	123-(-45-6789+AB)	BA-9*-876-5*-43-2+1
6847	11575	-1-23-4-5+6789+AB	-BA+9+8-76*-5*(43-21)
6848	11576	1-2-34+5+6789+AB	BA-98+(-76-54)*-3*21
6849	11577	1-(23+4+5-6789)+AB	B+A-9*(8-7*6+5^4/(-3/2+1))
684A	11578	-1+2-(34-5-6789-AB)	-BA-98*-76+5+43*21
684B	11579	-12-(-3-45+6+7-89*-A*-B)	B+A-9*-876-5*(-43-21)
6850	11580	1+2-34+5+6789+AB	B+A+(9+8-7)/(6*5-4^3)^-2-1
6851	11581	12-34-5+6789+AB	BA+9-8+(-7-65*4)*32*-1
6852	11582	1-(-2+3)-(4+5-6789)+A*B	B-A9*(8-7)*6-(5-4-32*-1)
6853	11583	-1-(23-4)-(-5-6789-AB)	-B*(-A+9)*(87+654-3+21)
6854	11584	-1-2-3+4-5+6789-A*-B	BA9+87*6+5432-1
6855	11585	-1-(-23+45-6789)+AB	BA9-87*-6-5432*-1
6856	11586	-12-3-4-5-(-6789-AB)	BA9+87*6+5432+1
6857	11587	1+23-45-(-6789-AB)	BA-9-((-8-(7-6^5/4)))*-3*2-1
6858	11588	1+2+3-4-5+6789+A*B	B-(A9-8+7)-(65*4*32-1)
6859	11589	123-45-(67-89*-A*-B)	-B-A*98*(7-6+54-3*21)
685A	11590	-1-2-(-3-45)-6-7+89*-A*-B	B+A+9-8*(7+6-(5+4)^3*2)^1
685B	11591	12-34-(-5-6789)+AB	-BA-9-87*(-65-4*3-21)
6860	11592	-12*3*(-45+6+7-89-AB)	B-(-A+9*-876+54-321)
6861	11593	-1-23+4+5+6789+AB	B+A-(9-(-8*-7-6^5/4))-4*3*2-1
6862	11594	-12-3-(-4-(-5+6789)-AB)	B*(A-(9-87)-(-654+3)+21)
6863	11595	1-23+4+5+6789+AB	B-A*(9-876)-543+21
6864	11596	12-(-34-5)-(-6+7+89*-A*B)	-BA-9*-876+5*4*(3+21)
6865	11597	12-3*-4567+89*A*-B	-B-A+9-8*7+6^5/4*3*2+1
6866	11598	123-45+6789+A-B	B+A+9-8*(7+6+(-5-4)^3*2-1)
6867	11599	-1+2-(-345+6-789*A)-B	-B+A9*(8-7)*6-5*4*(-3+2+1)
6868	11600	1+23*4-56-(-7-89*-A*-B)	BA-9*-876-5*-43+21
6869	11601	1*(2+3+4)*(-5+6+7-(-89A-B))	BA9-8*(-765-4*32+1)
686A	11602	-1-2+3*-4+5+6789+AB	B+A-9*(-8*-7-6^5/4)/(-4*-3)*2+1
686B	11603	12-3-(4-(5+6789)+A*-B)	B+A+9+(-8-(7-6^5/4))^3*2-1
6870	11604	-12-3+4+5+6789+AB	B+A+9+(-8-7+6^5/4)*-3*-2/1
6871	11605	-1-2-3+4-5+6789+AB	-B*(A98-76*(-5-(4-32)))-1
6872	11606	-1*(2-(-3+4)-(-5-(-6789-AB)))	BA-987*6+5*432*1
6873	11607	-1-2-3-4+5-(-6789-AB)	-BA-9+8*-7*6*-5*(4+3)+2*-1
6874	11608	-1+23-4-5+6789+A*B	-B+A-(-9+87)-(65*4*32+1)
6875	11609	1-(-2-3+4+5)-(-6789-AB)	B+A+9-(-8*-7-6^5/4)/-4*-3*2-1
6876	11610	1+23-4-5-(-6789+A*-B)	B+A+9-(-8*-7-6^5/4)/-4*-3*2^1
6877	11611	1+23-(4+5-6*7-89*-A*-B)	BA+987*6-5*(-432-1)
6878	11612	-1*(2-3)*(4-5)*(-6789-AB)	B-(A-9)-(87-65*-4*-32)+1
6879	11613	123-(45-67)+8*9AB	-B-(A+9*-876+5-4)+321
687A	11614	1*2*(3456+7+89-AB)	-B+A*9*-8*(-7-6)+5*(-4+321)
687B	11615	-1+2+3+4-5-(-6789-AB)	-B+A98*7-6+5*4*(32-1)
6880	11616	-1-(23-(45+6789))+A*B	B*(-A-9-8+765-4+3-(2-1))
6881	11617	1-(2+3)+4-(-5-6789-AB)	-B+A9+87+65*-4*(32-1)
6882	11618	1-(2+3*-4-(-5+6789))+AB	B+A-9+(-8+(-7+6^5/4)*3)*2^1
6883	11619	1*23-4+5+6789+A*B	-B-A-9-8*7-(-65*4*32-1)
6884	11620	123-(45-6789-A)+B	B+A-9-8*7+6^5/4*3*2*1
6885	11621	-12-3-(-4-5-67)-89*A*-B	B-A9*(8-(-7+6+54))*(-3*2+1)
6886	11622	-1*-2*(3456-(-78+9A-B))	B+A-9*(8-(7-6+5)^4-3+2)^1
6887	11623	1+2*3456+78-(-9+AB)	B-A98*7+6*-5*4*-3*-2*-1
6888	11624	12-3-4+5+6789+AB	-BA-98-(-76+54)*321
6889	11625	-1234+5-67+89*AB	-B+A98-7*-6*5*(43-2-1)
688A	11626	12+3*-4-5+67-89*-A*B	-BA+9-8*-7+65*4*32-1
688B	11627	123+45-6-7+8*9AB	B*(-A9-8-(-7+654)-(-3+2))^*-1
6890	11628	12+3-(-4+5-6789-AB)	-B-A+(-9+8-7-6^5/4-4*3)*2+1
6891	11629	-1+23-4-5+6789+AB	B+A98+(7+6)*(543+2+1)
6892	11630	12+3-4+5-(-6789-AB)	BA+9*8-76*-5*(4-3+21)
6893	11631	1+23-4-5-(-6789-AB)	B+A+(-9*-8*-7+6*(5+4)^3)*(2+1)
6894	11632	12-(3-4-5-(6789+AB))	B+A+9-8*7+(-6^5+4)*-3*2^1-1
6895	11633	-1-2+34+5+6789-A*-B	-BA+9-8-7-65*(4*-32-1)
6896	11634	-12+3+4+5-6*-7-89*A*-B	B+A+(-9-8+(-7+6+5)^4*3)*(2+1)
6897	11635	-1-23+4*5*-6-7-89*-A*B	B-A-98*(-76-5)-432*-1
6898	11636	-1-2*-3456+7-(-8+9A+B)	B+A+(-9(8+7)-6^5/4-4*3)*2-1
6899	11637	-1234+567*(8+9)+A*B	B+A+9-8*7+6^5/4*3*2-1
689A	11638	-1-2+3*45-(-6789+A-B)	-B*(A9+87-6*5*(4+32+1))
689B	11639	123+45-(-6+7)+8*9AB	-B-A9-87-(-6+5*-4)*321
68A0	11640	-1*(-23+4-(5+6789+AB))	-BA-9*(-876-(54+3))^2-1
68A1	11641	1-(-23+4)-(-5-(6789+AB))	B+A+(-9+8+(-7+6^5/4)*3)*2^1
68A2	11642	1234+5678-9+A-B	B-(A9+8*-7)+65*4*32*1
68A3	11643	-12+34-(-5-6789-AB)	-B+A-9*-8*7+6543+2-1
68A4	11644	123-4-5+6789-A+B	-B+A(9*8*-7-6543)+2*1
68A5	11645	-1-(23+4*-56)-(-7-8*9AB)	-BA+9*876-5-432*-1
68A6	11646	1-(2-3-(45+6789+A*B))	B+A-9+(-8-7-6^5/4-4*3)*2^1
68A7	11647	-1-(-23-4)-(-5-6789)+AB	-B-(A+9*8*-7-6543)+21

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
68A8	11648	$12*(3+4-(-567+89-AB))$	$-B+A*(-9+876-54-3)-2+1$
68A9	11649	$1+23+4-(-5-6789-AB)$	$B*(-A9+8-76-5+43*21)$
68AA	11650	$123-(-4+5)-(-6789-A+B)$	$BA+9+87+65*4*(32-1)$
68AB	11651	$123-(-4+5)-6789*(A-B)$	$-B-A-98-(-7-65*43*(2+1))$
68B0	11652	$12+34*5*-6+(-7+89)*AB$	$B+A-9+(-8+(7-6+5)^4*3)*(2+1)$
68B1	11653	$-1-2345+6-7*(8+9)*-AB$	$B+A+(-9-(8-7+6))*((-5-4)^3+2)*1$
68B2	11654	$-12+3+45+6789+AB$	$B+A+9*8+(-7-6^5/4)*-3*2-1$
68B3	11655	$12-3+45+6789+A*B$	$-B-A-9*(-876-5)-4+321$
68B4	11656	$1-2-(-34-(5+6789))+AB$	$-B-A98*-7+6+543-2*1$
68B5	11657	$-1-2*-3456+7*(-8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A98*-7+6+543-2+1$
68B6	11658	$123-(4+56-7)+89*-A*-B$	$B-A+9-8*7-65*-4*32*1$
68B7	11659	$-1-2-(3-45)-(-6789-AB)$	$-B-A-(9+8)-7-65*-4*-32*-1$
68B8	11660	$1234-(-5678-9)-(-A+B)$	$-B*A*(-9-(8+7))-((6+5)+4-3*21)$
68B9	11661	$1-2-3+45+6789+AB$	$B-A*(-9-876-(-54-(-3+21)))$
68BA	11662	$123+4+5+6789-A+B$	$B+A-9-8-7+6^5/4*3*2+1$
68BB	11663	$12+34-(-56+7)+89*-A*-B$	$-B-A+(-9+8+7)*((6^5/4+3)+2/1)$
6900	11664	$1+2+3*45-(-6789-A)+B$	$-B-(-A+9*(-8-765)-4*321)$
6901	11665	$1+2-(3-45)-(-6789-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7-6^5/4*3)/2^1-1$
6902	11666	$1+2+3-45*(-6-78-(-9+AB))$	$B+A-9*(8-7*(6-5*-4*3^2))-1$
6903	11667	$1+2+3+4-5+6+7-89*-A*B$	$-B-(A9-87+65*4*-32*1)$
6904	11668	$-1+2345-6*(-7-(89+A+B))$	$B+A9+8+76*-54*(-3+2-1)$
6905	11669	$-1-(-2-3)-(-45-6789-AB)$	$B-A*(9-876+54+3)+2*-1$
6906	11670	$1*2+3+45+6789+AB$	$-BA-(-98+7+65*-4*32+1)$
6907	11671	$1-(-234-5+67-8*9AB)$	$-B*(-A+9*8*7-6*5*43-21)$
6908	11672	$-1+234-(5-6789+AB)$	$B+A+9-8+(-7-6^5/4*3)*2/1$
6909	11673	$123+4*5+6789-A+B$	$B+A-9+(-8+7-6^5/4*3)*2-1$
690A	11674	$1-(-234+5-6789+AB)$	$B+A-9-8+7+6^5/4*3*2-1$
690B	11675	$123+4+5+67-8*-9AB$	$-BA+9+87-(-65*-4*-32-1)$
6910	11676	$12*-3*(-4+5*-67-8-(-9A-B))$	$B-(-A-9*876+5*-4-321)$
6911	11677	$-12+3*4*56*(7+8)+9*(-A-B)$	$B+A-9+8-7+6^5/4*3*2/1$
6912	11678	$-1*-2*(3456-(7-8+9-A-B))$	$-B+A-9-8-7-65*4*-32-1$
6913	11679	$1+2+3-4*56-7-8*-9AB$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^5/4*3*2^1$
6914	11680	$-1+2-(3-45)-(-67-89*A*B)$	$B+A+9-8-7+6^5/4*3*2+1$
6915	11681	$-1234-5-6-7+89*AB$	$B+A-9+(-8+7-6^5/4)*-3*2-1$
6916	11682	$123+4-(-5-6789)+A+B$	$-B*(-A9-(-8-(-7-654-3-2-1)))$
6917	11683	$-1*(-234-5-6789+AB)$	$B+A-9+8+(7-6+5)^4*3^2-1$
6918	11684	$1+234+5+6789-AB$	$B+A+(9+8+7-6*5)^4*3^2-1$
6919	11685	$-1*(-23+456)*(7+89-AB)$	$-BA+98+7+65*-4*-32*1$
691A	11686	$123+456-(78-9)*-AB$	$-BA-9-8*-7-65*43*(-2-1)$
691B	11687	$-1+2*(3456+7)-(-8-(9-(-A-B)))$	$BA9+8*76-5432*-1$
6920	11688	$12+34+5+67+89*A*B$	$BA9-8*-76+5432+1$
6921	11689	$-12+345-6-78*(9-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8*7*65+4321$
6922	11690	$-1*-2*(3456-(7+89)+AB)$	$-BA+98*(-7+6)*(-54+32*-1)$
6923	11691	$-1+23+45-(-6789-AB)$	$-B-A+9-8+7-65*4*-32*1$
6924	11692	$-1*(-23-45-6789-AB)$	$B+A+9-8+7+6^5/4*3*2-1$
6925	11693	$1+23+45+6789+AB$	$-B*(A-987+6+54*(3+2))*1$
6926	11694	$12-34*5+6789+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7+6^5/4*3*2+1$
6927	11695	$123+45-67+89*A*B$	$B-A-9-8+7+65*4*-32*-1$
6928	11696	$-123+45+(-678-9A)*-B$	$B+A+9+8-7+6^5/4*3*2+1$
6929	11697	$1^2+(-3-4)*(-5*-6*-7*8+9)+A-B$	$B-A+9-8-7-65*-4*-32*-1$
692A	11698	$(1+2*3)^4*5+(6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	$-B-A*9*-87+6+54*32+1$
692B	11699	$-1-2*-3456-(78-9-AB)$	$-B-A-98*-76+5-43*-21$
6930	11700	$1*2*(3-45)*(6+7-(8-9)-AB)$	$BA+9*876+5*(43+21)$
6931	11701	$-1-2*(-3*(-4+5^6+7)/8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7+6^5+4)*3/2+1$
6932	11702	$-1-2*-34+56+7+89*A*B$	$B+A+9-8-76*-5*(43-21)$
6933	11703	$-1234+5-(-6+7-89*AB)$	$B+A+9+8+(7-6+5)^4*3^2+1$
6934	11704	$123+45-(-6789-A)-B$	$B*(-A-9)*(-8-76+54+3-21)$
6935	11705	$123+45+6789*(-A+B)$	$-BA-9-(-8+7+65)*-4*(32+1)$
6936	11706	$123+45+6789-A+B$	$-BA9+8*-7-65*(4+3)*-21$
6937	11707	$-1234-5+6-(-7+89*-AB)$	$-B+A-9*(-876-54+3+2)-1$
6938	11708	$-1+23+45+67+89*A*B$	$-B-A*-987-6+5*(4-321)$
6939	11709	$123-(45-6789-A*B)$	$-B+A+98*76-5+43*21$
693A	11710	$-1+2*-3*4*-5+6789-A*-B$	$B-A-(-9+(8+7)*6*-5*(43-21))$
693B	11711	$-1-2*(-3456+78+9-AB)$	$B+A+9-8*7*-65+4321$
6940	11712	$1*-2*3*-4*(56*7-(89-AB))$	$B-A*(-9-8-7+6)*(54+3-2)+1$
6941	11713	$-1+23-(4*-56-7)-8*-9AB$	$BA-9*-876-54+321$
6942	11714	$-1-2+3*4567-8*9AB$	$BA+98*(7+65)+4*321$
6943	11715	$1-2*(-3+45)-(-678+9A)*-B$	$-B*(A9-876+5-(-4-32-1))$
6944	11716	$-1-23-45*6*7-89A*-B$	$B+A-9-8*(7-6*5*(4+3)^2^1)$
6945	11717	$-1-2*(-3-4)*(567+8+9+A+B)$	$BA+9*(876-(5-43)-2)+1$
6946	11718	$1*2*-3*(-456-7*-89)*(-A-B)$	$B+A+(9+8-(7-6))*((5+4)^3+2)+1$
6947	11719	$123+45+67+8*9AB$	$-B+A9-(87-65*4*32*1)$
6948	11720	$-1+2-34+(5-(678+9A))*-B$	$B+A-9*-876+54+321$
6949	11721	$123+45*-6-78*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A9*87-6*-5*-43-21$
694A	11722	$-1-23*(-4-5)+6789+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+76*-5*(-43+21)$
694B	11723	$-1-(-23-4)-(-5+6)-7*8*(9A)*-B$	$BA-(98+7)+65*-4*32*-1$
6950	11724	$-1+23*4+5+6789+AB$	$B+A+9+(-8-7+6^5/4*3)*-2^1$
6951	11725	$-1+234-5-6-7-8*-9AB$	$B+A+(-9+8-(-7-6^5/4)*3)*2^1$
6952	11726	$123+45-(-6789-A-B)$	$B*(-A+98-7+654+32+1)$
6953	11727	$1+2*(3456-78+9A+B)$	$B+A-9+8+(-7-6^5/4)*-3*2+1$
6954	11728	$-1+2+3+4-5+6*7*(8-(-9-AB))$	$B-A9*(-87+6)-(-543+21)$
6955	11729	$1-2+3-45*-6-7+8*9AB$	$B+A+9*((8-7)^6+5)^4+3+2-1$
6956	11730	$123-(45-6789-AB)$	$-B-A*(-9-876)-(-543-2)*1$
6957	11731	$12+3*4567+8*-9AB$	$B-(-A+98*-76+5+43*-21)$
6958	11732	$-123-45-(6+78)*(9-AB)$	$-B-(A+9*876-(-5*-4+3)*21)$
6959	11733	$123-(-4+5)+6-(-7+89*-A*B)$	$-B+A+9*(87-6)*5+4321$
695A	11734	$1+2*3456+78-(9-A)*-B$	$-BA98-7*6*(-543+2*1)$
695B	11735	$-1-(-234-5+6+7+8*-9AB)$	$-BA98+7*6*(543-2)+1$
6960	11736	$1+23*4+(56-789-A)*-B$	$B+A+(-9-(-8*-7+6))*-5*(4^3/2+1)$
6961	11737	$-1+234-(5-6)-(7+8*-9AB)$	$B*(A9-876-5+43)*(-2+1)$
6962	11738	$1-2*(-3456+7)-8+9A-B$	$BA-(98-7)-(-65*-4*32-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6963	11739	-1+234-5-6+7+8*9AB	-BA-9+8+(76-54)*321
6964	11740	1-234-56-(789+A)*B	-B+A9*87+6+543*-2*1
6965	11741	(-1-2*(3-4^5))*6-7*8*9+A-B	B+A-98*-76-(-5+43*-21)
6966	11742	1*2-3/-4*(5^6+7)+8+9+A-B	B+A+9*8+(-7-6^5/-4*3)*2-1
6967	11743	1-23*-4+5+67-89*-A*B	B-A+9-(-8-7*(6-(-54+3)))*21
6968	11744	12+3+45*6-7-8*-9AB	-B-A9+87+65*-43*(-2-1)
6969	11745	1+2-3+45-67*(-8-(9+AB))	-B-A-9+(876-543)*21
696A	11746	-1234+5+6*7-89*-AB	-B+A9*87+6*5*-43*(2-1)
696B	11747	-1-(2-3*45)+6789+A*B	-B+A+9*(876-5)+432+1
6970	11748	-1234+56-(7-89*AB)	-B*(-A+9)*(-8+765-4-3-2*1)
6971	11749	-1-2*-3-45*-6*-7-89A*-B	B-(-A-9-8)-(-7+65*4*32*-1)
6972	11750	1*234+5-(6-7)+8*9AB	B+A-(-9-8-7+65*4*-32-1)
6973	11751	1^2+(-3-4)*-5*-6*-7*8-9+A-B	BA+9-87-65*-4*32-1
6974	11752	1-2-3/-4*(5^6-(-7*8+9))+A-B	BA+9-87+65*4*32*1
6975	11753	1+2-(-3*45-6789)-A*-B	B-A+9*(876+54)-(3-(2-1))
6976	11754	1^2-3/-4*(5^6+7*8-9)+A-B	B+A+((9-8+7^6)/5-4^3)/2^1
6977	11755	-1-23+456+789*A+B	B+A9*(87-6)-543+2*1
6978	11756	-1+2*-3+4-(-5+678+9A)*-B	B-A98*-7+654+3*-21
6979	11757	-12-34+5*67-8*-9AB	BA-9*-876-(5*4-321)
697A	11758	1*2+(-3-(4^5/-6+7)*8)*9+A-B	B+A+9*8+(7-6+5)^4*3^2+1
697B	11759	1234+5678+9A-B	B*(A+98-7+654-3+21)
6980	11760	-12*(34-5)*(6+78+9-AB)	-BA9-8+7654+321
6981	11761	1+2-(3-456+789*-A+B)	B+A*(98+765-(43-21))
6982	11762	-1-2*-3456-(-7-89)-(-A+B)	B+A+9*(8+(7-6+5)^4)+3*2-1
6983	11763	1-2+3-(-456-789*A)-B	B+A+9*8+7+6^5/4*3^2-1
6984	11764	(1-2-(3*4-5)^6)/(7-8-9)+A-B	B+A+9*8+7+6^5/4*3^2^1
6985	11765	-1-2*-3456-7+(8-(9+A))*-B	-B+A-9+(-876+543)*-21
6986	11766	-12-3+456-789*-A+B	B+A+9*(8+(7-6+5)^4)+3^2^1
6987	11767	-123+4+56-78*(-9A-B)	BA9-8-(7+6)*(-543-2-1)
6988	11768	1+234-5*-6-7-8*-9AB	BA-9*-876-5-(4-321)
6989	11769	1*-2-(34-5*67)-8*-9AB	B+A-(9*(-876+5)-432-1)
698A	11770	-1-2*-3456-7*(-8+9*(A-B))	-B*-A*(9-8)*(-7+65-4*-3+21)
698B	11771	1234+5678+9A*B	B-A98*-7+654-32*1
6990	11772	12-3+456-789*-A-B	B-A9+8+(76-54)*321
6991	11773	-1234-(5-67)+89*AB	-B-A9*-8*7+6*5*-4*32*-1
6992	11774	1234+5678-9+AB	-BA9*(87+6-543)*2*-1
6993	11775	-1+2*3456-7+(-8+9)*AB	B+A+9*8*7+6*5^4*3^2(2-1)
6994	11776	-1234+5+(-6-7+89A)*B	-BA9+8+7654+321
6995	11777	1-2*-3456-7-(8-9)*AB	-B-A-9*-876-(-5-(432+1))
6996	11778	12+3+456-(-789*A+B)	-B+A*-98+7654-3*21
6997	11779	-12+3*(-45+6)*-78+9*-AB	B+A+9-(-8*-7+6^5)/-4*3*2+1
6998	11780	-1-2*-3456+(-7+8)*9A+B	B+A+(-9+8*7-6^5/-4*3)*2+1
6999	11781	1234+5678+9A+B	-B-A98*-7+654-(3+21)
699A	11782	-1+234-(5-6789+A+B)	BA+9*-8*-7+6543-2-1
699B	11783	1+2345-67-8*-9*A*B	B+A+9+(-8-(7+6^5/4))*-3*2-1
69A0	11784	123-4-(-5-6789-AB)	-BA98*7-(-6543+21)
69A1	11785	12-34-(5*-67+8*-9AB)	B-A+9-(-876+543)*21
69A2	11786	1*2*(3456-7*8*(9-A)+B)	BA*(-9-(-8+7*-6-54)+3-21)
69A3	11787	-1-23+45*-6+(-789+A)*-B	-B+A98*7+654+3-21
69A4	11788	1-2-345*-6+7*89A-B	B-A-9*-876-(5-432*1)
69A5	11789	1+23+456-(789*-A+B)	B+A+9*8*7+(6+5)*4^3(3+2)^1
69A6	11790	1+2*3+456-789*-A+B	B+A+9-8*-7*-6*5*(4-3)*^2(2-1)
69A7	11791	123+4-5-6+(-7-89*A)*-B	-BA-9*-876+5*(4*32-1)
69A8	11792	-1+234+5+6789-A-B	-B*(-A-9-87-(654-3)-21)
69A9	11793	-123+4*5*67-8*-9A*B	-BA98-7*6*-543-21
69AA	11794	1+234-(-5-6789+A)-B	B+A-9+8-(7-65*-43*(-2-1))
69AB	11795	1+234-5-67+89*-A*-B	-B-A+9+87+65*-4*-32*1
69B0	11796	1^2-3/-4*(5^6+7)+8*9+A-B	B+A-9*(-8*(-7-6)+5)*-4*3+2+1
69B1	11797	12+3*4*-5*-6+7-8*-9AB	BA-9*-876+5*4+321
69B2	11798	-12-34*-5+6789+AB	-B+A-(9-87-65*-4*-32-1)
69B3	11799	-123*(45+6-7+8-9A-B)	-B+A9+8*7*65+4321
69B4	11800	12+3+456-789*-A+B	B-A*98+7654-3*21
69B5	11801	123-4+5+67-89*A*-B	BA9-(-8-76*(-5-43))*2*-1
69B6	11802	1-(-2-3*-4-5*67-8*9AB)	-BA-98+76*(-54-3)*-2*1
69B7	11803	123+4*5+6789+AB	B+A98*7+654-3-21
69B8	11804	1*(-234+5-6789)*(A-B)	-B+A+9+8+7+65*-43*(-2-1)
69B9	11805	1+2-345+(-6-(-789-A))*B	-B+A98*7+65*-4*3*(-2+1)
69BA	11806	1-(-234+56-(-7-89*-A*B))	-BA-9*-876-(-543+2)+1
69BB	11807	-12+3*4-5+(-678-9A)*-B	-B-(-A9+8+7+65*4*32*-1)
6A00	11808	-12+3*-456-7-89*-AB	-BA-98*-7-(-6543+2)+1
6A01	11809	1+234*(56+78+9-AB)	-B-A98*-7+654-3+2+1
6A02	11810	1-2+345*6+7*89A+B	BA-9*8*-7+6543+21
6A03	11811	1+23+456-(-789*A-B)	-B+A98*7+654-(-3+2)+1
6A04	11812	-1+234+5+6789-(-A+B)	-B+A-(-98+7+65*-4*-32*-1)
6A05	11813	1-(-2-3)-4-(5*-67+8*-9AB)	B+A-9*8-7+6^5+4^3(3+2)-1
6A06	11814	-1*2*(-3456-78+(9-A)*-B)	BA-9-8*7*-65+4321
6A07	11815	123+45+6789-A*-B	-B-A*98+7654-32*1
6A08	11816	-1+234+56+7-8*-9AB	-B-A*98+7654-32+1
6A09	11817	1-2*(-3456-78+9-(A-B))	-BA98+7*6*543-2+1
6A0A	11818	12-3-4*-56-7-89*-A*B	B+A+9*876-(5+432)*-1
6A0B	11819	-1-2+345-67+8*9AB	B+A-9+87+65*-4*32*-1
6A10	11820	123-4*-5+67-89*A*-B	-BA98-7*-6*543+2*1
6A11	11821	-12+345+6789-AB	BA+9*(876+54)+3*3-21
6A12	11822	-1-2*-3456+78+9*A-B	-B+A9-8+7+65*4*32+1
6A13	11823	-1+2-(-345+67)+8*9AB	-B+A9+8-7-65*-4*32*1
6A14	11824	-12-34+56*7+8*9AB	B+A+(-9-8+7*(6-(-5-4)))^3)/2-1
6A15	11825	1+2+345-67+8*9AB	-B-(-A-98)+7-(65*-4*32+1)
6A16	11826	1+234-5+6789+A+B	-B+A+98+7-65*4*-32*1
6A17	11827	-1+234+5+67+8*9AB	B+A98*7+654-(3+2-1)
6A18	11828	(-1+2*3-(4^5/-6+7)*8)*9+A-B	B+A98*7+65*-4*-3(-2+1)
6A19	11829	1-(-234-5)+67+8*9AB	BA-9*-876-5*43*-2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6A1A	11830	-1234-5-67-89A*-B	B+A+9-8*(7-(-6+5-43))*-21
6A1B	11831	-1234-56-7-89A*-B	-B+A*-98+7654+3-21
6A20	11832	-1-2+345+6789-AB	-BA+9*876+543+21
6A21	11833	1*-2+345-(-6789+AB)	B+A98*7+654+3-2+1
6A22	11834	-1+234+5-(-6789-A-B)	-BA+98*7-(-6543-21)
6A23	11835	1+23*(4+5)+6789+A*B	-B+A9-8-7*(6+54-3)*-21
6A24	11836	123+45+6789+AB	-B-A*9*8+7654-321
6A25	11837	1*2+345+6789-AB	B+A*-98-(7654-32)*-1
6A26	11838	1+2-(-345-6789+AB)	BA-9+8-7+65*-4*32*-1
6A27	11839	-1+2-34-56*-7-8*-9AB	-B-A*-9+(-8-76)*-5*(-4-(-3-21))
6A28	11840	-1+23*(4+5)+(678+9A)*B	-B-A-9-8+7+6^5+4^4(3^2)-1
6A29	11841	1-(23-45)-(678+9A)*-B	BA-9*-876-(-54-321)
6A2A	11842	-12+345-(-6789-A*-B)	B+A+(-9*-8+7-6^5/-4*3)^2-1
6A2B	11843	12-34*-5+67-89*-A*B	BA+9-8-76*5*(-43+21)
6A30	11844	12*(3+4+5-6)*(-7+8+9+AB)	B-(-A9-(8-7+65*4*32))-1
6A31	11845	-1234-56+7+89A*B	B+A9-(-8+7)-65*4*32*-1
6A32	11846	1*-2*(-3456-(-7+89))-(A-B))	-B+A98*7+654+32-1
6A33	11847	1+2*(3456-7+89+A-B)	-B-A98*7-(-654-32*1)
6A34	11848	1*-2*(3456-7+89)*(A-B)	B+A+98+7+65*4*32*-1
6A35	11849	123-456+(-7+89)*-A*-B	BA+9*(876+5+43)+21
6A36	11850	-1-2*-3456+78-(-9A+B)	-B-A-9+(8+7+6*5+4^3)^2-1
6A37	11851	12+3-4-5*6+78*(9A+B)	B+A+(-9-8*7)*(6^5-5+4)*(3^2+1)
6A38	11852	1+(-2+3+4)*-5*-6*(7+8*9)-(A-B)	B-A98*7-65*4*3+21
6A39	11853	123+45+67+89*A*B	B-A98*-7+654-3+21
6A3A	11854	-1-23+4-56*7+8*9AB	-B-A-9-(-87-65*43*(2+1))
6A3B	11855	-1-23+4+5+6-78*(-9A-B)	-B+A*-98-(-7654-3-(-2+1))
6A40	11856	-1*(-2-(-34-56))*(7+8-9A-B)	B-A*-98-7*-6*-5*-43-21
6A41	11857	-1+2+345+6789-A*B	B+A-9*(-876-5)-(-432+1)
6A42	11858	123+4*56+7-8*-9AB	B*(A-9+876-5*(-4-(-32+1)))
6A43	11859	1+2+345+6789-A*B	B+A+9*8+7*(-6-5*(4+3))^2-1
6A44	11860	-1+2-(-345+6*7+8*-9AB)	-BA98+7*6*(543+2-1)
6A45	11861	1*2+345+6*7-8*-9AB	B+A+9-8*7*6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)
6A46	11862	-1*(-2345+6-7+8*-9*-A*-B)	B+A*-9*-8-7-(-6543+2-1)
6A47	11863	-12+3-4+56*7+8*9AB	BA+9+8+7*(6+5)*-4*-32*1
6A48	11864	-1-2-(3-4)*5-(6-78*(9A+B))	B+A-9*-8*7*(6-(-5+4^3)/2)-1
6A49	11865	-1+2*3456+78-9+AB	-B+A-(9+8)*(-7-(65+432*1))
6A4A	11866	1+2-3+456+78*(-9+AB)	-BA9+876*5+4321
6A4B	11867	-1234-5-6*7-89A*-B	B+A+9*8+7*((-6-5*(4+3))^2+1)
6A50	11868	1+2-(-345-67-(-8+9))*(A+B)	B-A9-(-87+65)*(4+321)
6A51	11869	(1*2+3)*(4+5*6*(7+8*9))+A-B	B+A*-98+7654-(3+2+1)
6A52	11870	12+345+6789-A*B	B+A98*7+654-(-32-1)
6A53	11871	-1-2*-3-(-456+78*(9-A-B))	-BA9-8*(-765-(432-1))
6A54	11872	-1+2-(3+4)-(-56*7-8*9AB)	B+A+(-9-8)*(7+(-6-5)*4^3)+2^1
6A55	11873	12-3*-456+7*(-8+9AB)	-B-A98+7*6*54*(3+2)*-1
6A56	11874	-12+345-6-7+8*9AB	-B-A9*-87+6+54*(3-21)
6A57	11875	-1-234-(-5+(-6-789+A)*B)	B+A+(-9+8*(7+6+(5+4)^3))^2^1
6A58	11876	1-(2-345*6)-7*(-89A-B)	B+A+(-9+8*(7+6+(5+4)^3))^2+1
6A59	11877	12-3+456+78*(-9+AB)	B+A+(-9*(-8+7*6+5^4)+3)*-2*1
6A5A	11878	-1+2-(-345*6+7*(-89A-B))	-BA9+8*(765+432)-1
6A5B	11879	-1+23*4*(5+67-89+AB)	-BA9+8*(765-432*-1)
6A60	11880	-123+456-7+8*9AB	-B*A*9*(-87-(6+5-43*2*1))
6A61	11881	1+23-(4-(-5-6))-78*(-9A-B)	B-A*-98+7*6*5*43*(-2+1)
6A62	11882	123-456+(789+A)*B	B+A-9-8+7+6^5+4^4(3^2)-1
6A63	11883	1234+5*6*7-8*9*-AB	B+A-9-8+7+6^5+4^4(3^2+1)
6A64	11884	-123+4*-567+89AB	BA98+765*(-4-3-2+1)
6A65	11885	(-1/(2+3)+4)*5^6(6-(-7+8))+9-(A-B)	B+A-9+8-7+6^5+4^4(3+2+1)
6A66	11886	-1-234-(-567+8*-9AB)	-B-A+9*(876-(-5-43-21))
6A67	11887	-1-(-23-45*6+7)+89*A*B	B+A+9-8-7+6^5+4^4(3+2+1)
6A68	11888	1-(234-567)-8*-9AB	BA+9*(876-5)-(-432+1)
6A69	11889	-1-2-3*-4+5*(-6-78-9A)*-B	-B-A98*-7-6*(5+43)*(-2-1)
6A6A	11890	1-2-34*(5+67)+89AB	-B-A*98+7654+32-1
6A6B	11891	12+3-4+56*7+8*9AB	-B-A9*-87-654-321
6A70	11892	12+3-(4-5-6)-78*(-9A-B)	-BA9+8+7-6*-5*(-4+321)
6A71	11893	-1234+56-(-7+89A)*-B	BA-9+8*(7-65)*(4+3)*(-2-1)
6A72	11894	-123+456+7+8*9AB	BA+9*(876+54)-3-(-2+1)
6A73	11895	(1+(2+3)^4)*(5+6+7-(-8-9))-(A-B)	B+A+(9-8)^7+6^5+4^4(3^2)+1
6A74	11896	1*-2*(-3456-78-9-A-B)	BA-9*(876+54)*(-3+2*1)
6A75	11897	((1+2+3)^4-5*6*7*8)*9+A-B	-BA9+8*7*(65+4)*3-2*-1
6A76	11898	-1*2*(-3456-(-7+8-9)-AB)	-B-A*(-98-765)+43*-2+1
6A77	11899	1234+5-6-78*(-9A+B)	B-(-A9-8*7-(65*4*32-1))
6A78	11900	1+2*34*56+7*-8*-9A+B	B-A+9-(-8+(-76+54)*321)
6A79	11901	-123+4*5-(-6-7+89)*-AB	B+A*987-(65+4+3)*21
6A7A	11902	12+345-(6+7+8*-9AB)	B*(-A-9-8+765-4+3+21)
6A7B	11903	-1+2-(-345+6-7)-8*-9AB	-B-A-9*-876+543-21
6A80	11904	1-(2+34-5*6*7)-89*-A*B	B-A98*-7-65*(4*3-21)
6A81	11905	-1-2-3-(4-5*(678+9AB))	-B-(A+98*7-6543)-21
6A82	11906	-1234+5-6-7+89A*B	B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)
6A83	11907	1*23*(4-(56-78)-9)*(A+B)	B+A+(-9*(-8-7)*(-6-5)*-4+3)^2^1
6A84	11908	1*-2*(-34+56)*(7-89-AB)	-B+A*(-9+8-76)*-5+4321
6A85	11909	-1+2-3-4+5*(678+9AB)	B+A-9*((-8*7*-6+5)*4+3)-(-2-1)
6A86	11910	1+23+4+56*7+8*9AB	B+A+9+(8+7+6*5+4^3)^2-1
6A87	11911	1234+5+6-78*(-9A+B)	BA-9+(-87+65)*(4-321)
6A88	11912	-1*2*(-3456+7-8-9A-B)	B+A+9+(8+7+6*5+4^3)^2+1
6A89	11913	1-2-(-345-6-7)+8*9AB	B+A9+87-654-321
6A8A	11914	12+345+6-(7+8*-9AB)	-B-A98-(-7654-321)
6A8B	11915	1-(-234+5)-(-6789+A*-B)	B+A+(-9/-8+7)*(6+(5+4)^3*2)-1
6A90	11916	123+45-67*(-8-9-AB)	-B-A+9*876+5*-4*-32-1
6A91	11917	1+2-(-345-6)-(-7+8*-9AB)	-BA98+7*-654*(-3-2)+1
6A92	11918	12-(3-4*-56*7-89*AB)	B+A+9+8+7+6^5+4^4(3^2)+1
6A93	11919	-1+2+34-(-56*7-8*9AB)	B+A9-87-(6-5*-4)*-321
6A94	11920	-1*-2*(-3-(-4+5*-678-9*AB))	B+A9*8-7*(-6-543)*2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6A95	11921	$1-2^*-34^*(-56-(78-9))^*(A-B)$	$-BA9+8765+43^*-21$
6A96	11922	$-1234-5+6+7-89A^*-B$	$-BA-9^*-87+6543-2^*1$
6A97	11923	$-1+234+5+6789-A^*-B$	$B+A+((-9-8)^*-7-6^{\wedge}5/-4^*3)^*2^{\wedge}1$
6A98	11924	$-12-(3+4)-(-5^*6^*7-89^*A^*B)$	$-B+A9^*87-65-43^*21$
6A99	11925	$1+234+5-(-6789-A^*B)$	$B-A-9^*-876+543-21$
6A9A	11926	$-12+345^*6-7^*(8-9A^*B)$	$-B+A9-(-87-65^*4^*32-1)$
6A9B	11927	$1-2+(3+4^*-56)^*7-89^*-AB$	$-B-A+98^*7+6543-2-1$
6AA0	11928	$-12^*-3^*(4+56-(-78+9)+AB)$	$-BA^*(9-8-76-(-5+4)-(-3-(2-1)))$
6AA1	11929	$-12+345+6^*7+8^*9AB$	$-B-A-9^*-876+543+2-1$
6AA2	11930	$-1^*-2^*(3456+7-8+9+AB)$	$B+A9^*-8+7^*(654-3)^*2+1$
6AA3	11931	$-12+345+6789-A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*4-3-2-1$
6AA4	11932	$123-45-(678+9A)^*-B$	$B+A+9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*-4-3^*2+1$
6AA5	11933	$12+34+5+6+7+8^*(9A+B)$	$-B-A-9^*-8+(76-54)^*321$
6AA6	11934	$-1+234-5+6789+AB$	$B-A9-8-76^*(-54-3)^*-2^*-1$
6AA7	11935	$-1^*(2+3)^*(4-5-6-78-9A)^*B$	$BA+9^*(876+54)-(-32-1)$
6AA8	11936	$1+234-5+6789+AB$	$B-A98+7654+321$
6AA9	11937	$12+3^*(-4-56)-(-789-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7^*(-6^*-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2)^*1$
6AAA	11938	$12-3+45+6-78^*(-9A-B)$	$BA-9^*-876+5-(-432+1)$
6AAB	11939	$1+2^*3456-(-78+9A)^*-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$
6AB0	11940	$1^*-2-(-3-4^*(-5-6^*-7^*8))^*9+A-B$	$BA-9-(-87+65^*4^*32^*1)$
6AB1	11941	$1+2345+67+8^*-9^*A^*-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$
6AB2	11942	$-1-(2-345)-(-6789+AB)$	$-B+A9^*-8+7654-32-1$
6AB3	11943	$1+((-2^*-3)^{\wedge}4-(-5^*6+7)+8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-A9^*8-(7654-32)^*-1$
6AB4	11944	$-1+234+5+6789+AB$	$B+A+9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*-4+3^*2+1$
6AB5	11945	$1^*234+5-(-6789-AB)$	$-BA9+8+7^*(-65-4+3)^*-21$
6AB6	11946	$1-(-234-5-6789-AB)$	$-B^*(A+9-(-8-76-54))^*(-3-2-1)$
6AB7	11947	$-12-3-4^*-5^*6^*7-8^*9A^*-B$	$B+A+98^*7-(-6543+21)$
6AB8	11948	$1+2+345+6789-A-B$	$-B-A+9-8^*(-7-6)^*-5^*(-4^*3^*2+1)$
6AB9	11949	$1-2^*-34^*(-5+6)+78^*(9A+B)$	$-B+A-98^*-7+6543-(2-1)$
6ABA	11950	$-1+234+5+6+7-89^*A^*-B$	$B+A+(9^*8+7)^*(6+(5+4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
6ABB	11951	$-12+345-(-6789-(A-B))$	$B-(A-98^*7-(6543-2+1))$
6B00	11952	$1-(-234-56-7+89^*A^*-B)$	$BA+9^*-8+(-76+54)^*-321$
6B01	11953	$-12+345-(-6789-(-A+B))$	$-B-A^*(-98-765+4)-(-3-(-2-1))$
6B02	11954	$123+456-789^*-A+B$	$-BA+9^*8^*-7^*(6+5-(-4+3))^*2^*-1$
6B03	11955	$12+3-(-4-56)+78^*(9A+B)$	$BA+98-7-65^*-4^*32^*1$
6B04	11956	$1-2+345-678^*(9-(A+B))$	$B+A^*(987-65)+43^*-21$
6B05	11957	$-1-2^*-34-56^*-7+8^*9AB$	$B^*(-A9-(-876+54-32))^*1$
6B06	11958	$-1-234-56-(789+A)^*-B$	$BA-(-9-87+65^*4^*32^*1)$
6B07	11959	$12+345+6789-A-B$	$-B+A9^*-8-(-7654-(3-21))$
6B08	11960	$1^*(-23+4)^*(-56-7+8)^*(9+A-B)$	$-B-A-98^*-76-(543^*-2+1)$
6B09	11961	$-1^*-23^*(456-(78+9A-B))$	$-B-A98^*-7-6^*-5^*-4^*3^*(-2-1)$
6B0A	11962	$-1-2+345-(-6789-(A-B))$	$B+A-9^*((-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*4-3)-2^{\wedge}1$
6B0B	11963	$-1-2+345+6789^*(-A+B)$	$-B^*-A+(-9+8^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3))^*2-1$
6B10	11964	$1-(2-345-6789-(A-B))$	$B+A-9^*((-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2-1))$
6B11	11965	$123+4+(56+7^*-8)^*-9^*-AB$	$-B+A^*(98+765)-(-4+32)^*1$
6B12	11966	$-1+2+345+6789+A-B$	$B+A-9^*((-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*4-3)+2^{\wedge}1$
6B13	11967	$-1+2-(-345+6789^*(A-B))$	$B+A+(-9-(-8^*7-6^{\wedge}5/4))^*3^*-2^*1$
6B14	11968	$1-(-2-345-6789-A+B)$	$B+A-(9+8^*7)+65^*4^*(32+1)$
6B15	11969	$-123-4-(-5-6)-(-789-A)^*-B$	$-B-A-(-9+8^*7-6-54)^*(3-21)$
6B16	11970	$1-(-2-345-(6789-A))+B$	$BA+9^*8+7+65^*-43^*(-2-1)$
6B17	11971	$12+345+678^*(-9+A+B)$	$B+A+9^*876-(-543-2+1)$
6B18	11972	$(-1-(2+(-3-4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A-98^*-7-6543^*(-2+1)$
6B19	11973	$-12+345-(-6789-A)+B$	$-B-A+9876-54^*3^*21$
6B1A	11974	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5+6^*7-8^*9A-B$	$BA-98^*(-7-65+4+3-21)$
6B1B	11975	$1-(-2+34+56^*-7^*(-89+AB))$	$BA-9^*-8+76-54)^*321$
6B20	11976	$123+4-(-56-789)^*A+B$	$B+A+(-9^*8+(7+6+5^*4)^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
6B21	11977	$-1234+56+7-89A^*-B$	$-B-A9^*8-(-7654+3+2-1)$
6B22	11978	$123-4-(5^*-6^*-7-8^*9AB)$	$B+A-9+(-8+(7/(6-5))^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2)+1$
6B23	11979	$12+345+6789+A-B$	$-B^*(A-98-765+43^*2^*1)$
6B24	11980	$1+2^*(34+56)^*-7^*-8+9A-B$	$BA+9^*(876+5)+432+1$
6B25	11981	$12+345-(-6789+A)+B$	$B+A9^*-8+7654+3-21$
6B26	11982	$1-23-4-(-5-6-(-789+A))^*-B$	$-BA+9+87+65^*4^*(32+1)$
6B27	11983	$1-234^*-5-6^*7+8^*9A^*B$	$-B-A-98^*-76+543^*-2^*-1$
6B28	11984	$-1-(2-345)-(-6789-A)+B$	$-B-A+(-9-8+7-6+5)^{\wedge}4^*(3+2/1)$
6B29	11985	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6^*7-8+9+A+B$	$B+A^*(98+765)-4^*3^*(2+1)$
6B2A	11986	$1-2+345+6789+A+B$	$-B-A+9^*((8^*7+6)^*5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
6B2B	11987	$-1+2^*3^*-4+(-5-6)^*(-789+A+B)$	$-B+A9^*(8-(-76+5))-(-4-(-3-2))^*-1$
6B30	11988	$-1+2+345+6789+A+B$	$B+A-((-9-(8+7^*-6^*5))^*(-4^{\wedge}3+2))-1$
6B31	11989	$1-23^*(4-5-6^*7^*8-(9A-B))$	$B+A^*(98+765)-4-(3+21)$
6B32	11990	$123-45^*(6-(-7+89)-AB)$	$-B^*(A+9-(-8+765)-(-4+3+21))$
6B33	11991	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+(-8+7+6^*5+4)^{\wedge}3/(2+1)$
6B34	11992	$-1+2345-6^*(-7-(89+A))^*B$	$B+A-9^*((-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*4-3^*2)+1$
6B35	11993	$-12-(34+5)-(-6-7+89)^*-AB$	$-B-(-A-9876+54^*-3^*-21)$
6B36	11994	$12+345-(-67-8^*9AB)$	$B+A-9^*((-8+7)/-6^*(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-(-2-1))$
6B37	11995	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6-7)^{\wedge}8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*876+543+21$
6B38	11996	$1-234-5^*6-(-789+A)^*-B$	$B+A-9-8^*-7^*((6/(5-4))^{\wedge}3-2/1)$
6B39	11997	$1-(2+3)-(-4+(-5+6+78))^*(-9A-B))$	$B+A+9/8^*(7+6+5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
6B3A	11998	$-1234+5+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9/8^*(7^*6-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2/1$
6B3B	11999	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6-(7-8)^{\wedge}9+A-B$	$B-A^*-987+65^*(-43+21)$
6B40	12000	$-1-2^*-34-(-5+6+7+8+9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9^*(8-7+6+5+4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
6B41	12001	$12+345+6789+A+B$	$-B^*(A98-7-6^*5^*4^*(-3+21))$
6B42	12002	$1+2-3+45^*-6+(-7-89)^*-A^*B$	$B+A+98^*76+543^*2-1$
6B43	12003	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5+6+7/(8-9)+A-B$	$B+A9^*-8+7654^*(-3+2)^*-1$
6B44	12004	$1234+5-67^*(-8-9A)-B$	$B+A+(-9+(-8^*-7+6^{\wedge}5/4)^*3)^*2+1$
6B45	12005	$1234-5-67^*(-89-A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(-876-54-3-21)$
6B46	12006	$1-(-2-3)-4^*-5^*6^*(-7-(-8-9^*-A+B))$	$B-A9^*8+(-7654-3)^*(-2+1)$
6B47	12007	$1+2^*-3^*(45+67^*(89-AB))$	$-B+A-(-98+7^*-6)^*(5-4+3^*21)$
6B48	12008	$1-2-3^*(-45+6)-78^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A9^*-8+7654-3^*-2-1$
6B49	12009	$-12-3^*(456+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A-9-(8+(-7^*(6-5))^{\wedge}4)^*(-3-2/1))$
6B4A	12010	$1-23^*4^*(-5-(-6+7)-89)+A+B$	$B+A-9^*(8-(-7^*-6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
6B4B	12011	$-1+2^*-34^*-5-(-6789-AB)$	$B-A9^*-8^*7-6^*(-543-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
6B50	12012	$-1 * (-23+4 - (-5+678) - 9A) * B$	$-B * (-A98 - (7-654) - 321)$
6B51	12013	$-12-34-56+(-789+A) * -B$	$B+A+9-8*7 * ((-6*(5-4))^{3+2}) - 1$
6B52	12014	$-123+456-7-89*A*-B$	$B+A9-8-(76-54)*-321$
6B53	12015	$1+((-2*3)^4+5-(-6*7+8)) * 9+A-B$	$B+A+9876+54*3*21$
6B54	12016	$1-23*(456+78+9*-AB)$	$B+A+(-9*-8*-7*-6-5^4)*(3+2^1)$
6B55	12017	$(1-2^3)^4*5+6-7*(8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6+5^4)^3/(2+1)$
6B56	12018	$1*-2*(-3+4-5*(-67+89A+B))$	$B-A*(-98-765+4)-(-32+1)$
6B57	12019	$-1-23*4*-5+6789+A-B$	$-B+A9*-8+7654-32*-1$
6B58	12020	$1+2*3+4*-5*6+(-789+A)*-B$	$-B-(A+9*-87-6543)-21$
6B59	12021	$1+23-4+(5-6-78)*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A9-(-87*-6*5*-4+321)$
6B5A	12022	$1-2-3*(456+7)+89A*B$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7+6^5/4)/-3*2+1$
6B5B	12023	$-12+3*-456-7+89A*B$	$-B*(-A9-(-8+7)-(654-(-32+1)))$
6B60	12024	$123-4-5-6+78*(9A+B)$	$B+A-9*(-8+7)/-6*(-5*4)^3+2+1$
6B61	12025	$1-23-(-456+7)+8*9AB$	$B-A9*8+7654-3+21$
6B62	12026	$-12*(-34-567-(8-9+A+B))$	$B+A+(9-8+7-6+5)^4*(3+2/1)$
6B63	12027	$-1-23+4*-567+89AB$	$B+A+9-(8+7+65*4*(-32-1))$
6B64	12028	$-123+456+7+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+9*(8*7+6)*5+4^3(3+2))+1$
6B65	12029	$1-23+4*-567+89AB$	$B+A9*-8*-7-6+54*-3*-21$
6B66	12030	$(1^2+3)^4*(5+6*7)+8-9+A-B$	$-B-(A98-7-6*5*(-4+321))$
6B67	12031	$-1-2^3(3^4)+5^6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-(-8*-7+6^5/4)*-3*2+1$
6B68	12032	$-123+4-(-56+(-789+A)*B)$	$-B+A*(98+765)-4-(-32+1)$
6B69	12033	$1-2^3(3^4)+5^6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(9*-8+7-6^5/4)*-3*2^1$
6B6A	12034	$-12+345+6+7-89*A*-B$	$-B*(A+9-8*-7-6-5^4*321)$
6B6B	12035	$123-4-(-5+6)*78*(-9A-B)$	$-B-A*-9*(87-6*-5)-(-43-21)$
6B70	12036	$12+345-6-7+89*A*B$	$B+A-9*(-8*(-7-6-5*-4*3^2)+1)$
6B71	12037	$-1+2+345-6+7+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8*-7*-6-5*4)*(3+2-1)$
6B72	12038	$-12-3+4*-567+89AB$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*6-(5+4)^3*2-1)$
6B73	12039	$-1+2+3+45*-6+(789+A)*B$	$B+A-9+8-7*(6+5+(-4*3)^2(2+1))$
6B74	12040	$12*(-3+4)*5(-6-78*9)+A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7-6*((-5+4^3)*2+1))$
6B75	12041	$-1-23*4*-5-(-6789-A-B)$	$B-A*(-9-876-(-5-4-32-1))$
6B76	12042	$123-(-4-5+6)-78*(-9A-B)$	$B-(A-9*87-6543+21)$
6B77	12043	$1-23*-4-(-56+78*(-9A-B))$	$-B-A+98*(7-6-5)*(-43+21)$
6B78	12044	$-1*-2*(3456+7*8+9+AB)$	$-B+A*(98+765+4)+3*2-1$
6B79	12045	$1234+5*-67-8*-9A*B$	$B-(A+9)-8-76*(-54-3)*2+1$
6B7A	12046	$1-2*3+456-7+8*9AB$	$-B-A9*-8*-7+6+543*21$
6B7B	12047	$1-2+345+6+7-89*A*-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7)-6-(-5*4-3)^2(2+1)$
6B80	12048	$-12-(3-(456+7-8*-9AB))$	$B+A-9*8+(7-6*5^4+3)^2-1$
6B81	12049	$-12+3*-456*-7+8-9AB$	$-BA9-87-6*5*(-4+321)$
6B82	12050	$-1*-2*(3456+78+9A-B)$	$B+A-9*8+(7-6*5^4+3)^2+1$
6B83	12051	$-1-2+3+456-7+8*9AB$	$B+A-9-(8-7*(6+5*(4+3)^2(2+1)))$
6B84	12052	$-1*(-2+3+456+7*-89)*AB$	$-B+A*(9+876+5-4)-321$
6B85	12053	$1-2+3+456-7-8*-9AB$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+(6+5+4*3)^2(2+1)$
6B86	12054	$-12*(-34-(5+678-(9+AB)))$	$B+A+9*(8+(7^6(6-5)+4)^3-2/1)$
6B87	12055	$-1+2+3+456-7+8*9AB$	$B+A+9*(8-((-7*(6-5)-4)^3+2))+1$
6B88	12056	$-1*-2*(-3+456-78-9A)*B$	$B+A*-98*-7-65*-43-2*1$
6B89	12057	$1-2+3+4*-567+89AB$	$B+A-9-(8+(-7*(6-5))^4)*(-3-2)*1$
6B8A	12058	$-1*(-23-45*(67+8-(-9-AB)))$	$B+A-9-(-8/(7*(6-5)))^4*(3+2)+1$
6B8B	12059	$1+23-45*(-67-8-(9+AB))$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+6+(5*4+3)^2(2+1)$
6B90	12060	$1-2*3+456-(-7-8*9AB)$	$BA-9*-876-5*4*(-32+1)$
6B91	12061	$1+2+3-(-4*-567-89AB)$	$B-A*(-98-765-4+3-2-1)$
6B92	12062	$12+345+6+7+89*A*B$	$-BA9-87+6*-543*(-2-1)$
6B93	12063	$-1+2-3+456+7+8*9AB$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*-6+5)*-4^3/2+1$
6B94	12064	$1*-2*(34-56)*78-(-9-AB))$	$-B+A-9*-87-(-6543+2-1)$
6B95	12065	$1+2-3+456-(-7+8*-9AB)$	$B-A-98*(-7+6+5)*(-43+21)$
6B96	12066	$12+34-56*-7-89*A*-B$	$B+A+9*876-(-543+21)$
6B97	12067	$-123-456+78*(9+AB)$	$B+A9*(87-6)+(-5+4)*321$
6B98	12068	$-1-2-(-3+4)+5+(-6+789-A)*B$	$BA-98*-7+6543-21$
6B99	12069	$-1+2+3-(-456-7+8*-9AB)$	$-BA+9*(876+54)+321$
6B9A	12070	$-1-2*-3+456+7+8*9AB$	$-B-A+9*87+6543+21$
6B9B	12071	$1-(-2-3)-(-456-7)+8*9AB$	$B+A*9*(8+76+54-3-21)$
6BA0	12072	$12+3+4*-567+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+(7+6*5-4)^3/(2+1)$
6BA1	12073	$-1-2-(-345-6789)+A*B$	$B+A+9*(8+(7^6(6-5)+4)^3)+2-1$
6BA2	12074	$-1-(2-345-6*7-89*-A*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8*7-6^5/4)*-3*2-1$
6BA3	12075	$1-(2-(345+6789+A*B))$	$B+A+(9*-8+7-6^5/4)*-3*2^1$
6BA4	12076	$12-3+456+7-8*-9AB$	$B-A*-987-65*(-4+3)*-21$
6BA5	12077	$12+3-(-4+5)*(67+8-9AB)$	$-B+A*(98+765+4)+32*1$
6BA6	12078	$1-(2-3*4)-56-(789-A)*-B$	$-B+A9*87+65+43*-21$
6BA7	12079	$1+2+345+6789-A*-B$	$-B+A98*7-65+43*21$
6BA8	12080	$1+2+3-45-6-(789-A)*-B$	$-BA-9*(87-6)*(5+4+3+2)*-1$
6BA9	12081	$-1+23-4*567+89AB$	$B+A+9*876+5*4*32+1$
6BAA	12082	$12+3+456+7*-8*-9AB$	$BA-98*-76-5*-4*-3*-21$
6BAB	12083	$-12-(-345-6789-AB)$	$-B-A98-7*(-65-4+3)*21$
6BBA	12084	$1*-2*(34-56*78-9+A-B)$	$B+A+9*87-(-6543+2)-1$
6BB1	12085	$(1-2^3)^4*5+(-6+7+8)^9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8*7*6^5(5+4-3*2)+1$
6BB2	12086	$123+45-6-78*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A-9*(-876-54-32+1)$
6BB3	12087	$1+23*(-45+6)+789A-B$	$B+A-9*8+7*6*(5+4*3)^2/1$
6BB4	12088	$-1-2-345+(67-(-8-9)) * AB$	$B-A-9*(-876-54-32+1)$
6BB5	12089	$1+234+5*6*7-89*-A*B$	$B*(A9-876-5-4-3-2)*-1$
6BB6	12090	$12+345-(-6789-A*B)$	$-B-(-A-9*87-(6543+21))$
6BB7	12091	$-1+23+456+7+8*9AB$	$B-A*-98-(-7+65)*4*(-32-1)$
6BB8	12092	$12-3*(-45-6+78)*(9-AB)$	$B-A-9*-87-(-6543-21)$
6BB9	12093	$-12+34-56-(-789+A)*B$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6)+(5*4+3)^2(2+1)$
6BBA	12094	$-1-(2-345-6789-AB)$	$BA-9*-876-(-543-2-1)$
6BBB	12095	$1+2-(34-5)-6-(789-A)*-B$	$BA9-(-876-5*4*321)$
7000	12096	$1-2+345+6789+AB$	$B+A+(9*8*7*6*5)*4-(3-2)/1$
7001	12097	$-1+(-2+(-3-4)*5)*(-6*7*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7*6)*-5*(4+3)+2-1$
7002	12098	$-1-(-2-345-6789-AB)$	$-B-A*(-98-765-4-3*2)-1$
7003	12099	$-1*(234+5-6)*78-9A-B$	$B+A+(-9+(-8-7)*6)*(5-4^3*2+1)$
7004	12100	$1+2+345+6789+AB$	$B*A*(9+8-(-7+6)-(-54-3)+21)$
7005	12101	$(1-2^3)^4*5-(-6-7)*8-9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-987+6)*(-5-4)-321$
7006	12102	$1234-5+6-7*(-8-9AB)$	$-BA9-8-7-6*-5*(4+321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7007	12103	$1-2-3-45^*-67+8^*9^*-A^*-B$	$-B-A9+8^*76^*(5+4^*3)-(-2-1)$
7008	12104	$-1+2345-67^*-89-AB$	$B+A-9-8+(7-6^*5^*4+3)^2*1$
7009	12105	$1^*2345-67^*-89-AB$	$B+A-9-8+(7-6^*5^*4+3)^2+1$
700A	12106	$12+3+4^*-56-(-789-A)^*B$	$B+A-9-8^*7^*(-6^*(5-4))^3-2^2*1$
700B	12107	$((1+2)^3+4^5)/(-6+7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$BA-98^*-76-(54-3)^*-21$
7010	12108	$1-(2^3-4^*(5-6^*-7^*8^*9))+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4-3^*2^*1)$
7011	12109	$123+4+56+78^*(9A+B)$	$-B+A^*9+(8+7)^*(6+543+21)$
7012	12110	$-12^*(-34-567+89-AB)$	$BA98-765-4321$
7013	12111	$12-(-345-6789-AB)$	$-B^*(-A-987-65^*-4)+3-2-1$
7014	12112	$-1-2^*-3-45^*-67-8^*9^*-A^*B$	$B+A-9+(8+7^*6+5^*4^*3)^2*1$
7015	12113	$1-2+345+67+89^*-A^*-B$	$-B+A+9^*(-8-76+543)^*-2^*-1$
7016	12114	$1/(2-3)+4^*(5+6^*7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A+98^*76+(-54-3)^*-21$
7017	12115	$-12-3-(4^*-56+78^*(-9A-B))$	$B+A-9^*8-7+6+(5^*4+3)^(2+1)$
7018	12116	$-1^*-2^*(3456+78-(-9-AB))$	$-BA9-8+7+6^*-5^*(-4-321)$
7019	12117	$-1+234-(-56+7^*8)^*9^*AB$	$B+A+9^*8^*7^*(6-5)^*4^*3^*2/1$
701A	12118	$-1-2^*(-3-4)^*567-8^*-9A-B$	$-B-A9-87^*(-65-(4+32))+1$
701B	12119	$(1-2^3)^4*5-(-6-7)^*8+9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9+8+(7-6^*5^*4+3)^2-1$
7020	12120	$-1-2-34-5^*-6+(789-A)^*B$	$B+A+(9-8-7^*6-5-4^3)^2-1$
7021	12121	$1-23-4^*-5-6+(-789+A)^*-B$	$-B+A^*9-87-6^*-54^*-3-21$
7022	12122	$-1-2^*(3-4^5*6+7+8^*9)+A-B$	$-B^*(A+9)^*(-8-76+5-(4-32-1))$
7023	12123	$1^*-23^*(-456+78-9+A^*B)$	$-BA+9+87^*(65+4+32)-1$
7024	12124	$12^*(-3+45-(-678+9+AB))$	$-B-A+9+(-8^*7-6^*-54)^*(32-1)$
7025	12125	$-1+2345+67^*89-A^*B$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4-3^*2)-1$
7026	12126	$1+2-34-5^*-6-(789-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9^*(876+54+32+1)$
7027	12127	$-1-2^*-3+4^*56^*-7-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4-3^*2)+1$
7028	12128	$1-2+3+4-5-6-(-789+A)^*B$	$B+A+9-8^*7^*(-6^*(5-4))^3+2^2*1$
7029	12129	$-1+234-56-78^*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A^*987+(654-3)^*2^*-1$
702A	12130	$-1^*-2^*((-3-4^5)^*6-7^*8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7^*6+5^*4^*3)^2*1$
702B	12131	$1234-5^*-6-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$-BA+98^*76+5-4^*-321$
7030	12132	$-1-2-3+4-5+6+(-789+A)^*-B$	$B-(A+9^*-8^*7)+65^*(4^*32-1)$
7031	12133	$-1^*(23-(-4+5+6-(-789-A)))^*B$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(-876+54+3^*21)$
7032	12134	$-1+2^*-34+567-8^*-9AB$	$-BA-9-87^*-6^*5^*4-3^*21$
7033	12135	$12-3^*456-(-7-89A)^*B$	$-BA-9^*8^*-7^*6-(-5432+1)$
7034	12136	$-1^*234^*(5+67+8-9A-B)$	$BA+9876-54^*-3^*-21$
7035	12137	$-1+2^*(3+4)^*567-8^*(-9-A^*B)$	$B+A+9+8+(7-6^*5^*4+3)^2-1$
7036	12138	$-1^*2^*(-3456-(7+89+AB))$	$B+A+9+8+(7-6^*5^*4+3)^2*1$
7037	12139	$1-2^*(-3456-7-89-AB)$	$B-A^*(98+76)^*-5-4^*-321$
7038	12140	$1+234-5^*-67-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A9^*(-87+6)+54^*3^*-2^*1$
7039	12141	$-123^*(45-(-6-7+8+9A)-B)$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^*(5+4^*3)^2-1$
703A	12142	$-1-(-2-(3-4^5/-6-7))^*-8^*-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^*(5^*4-3)^2/1$
703B	12143	$12+3+4-5-6+(789-A)^*B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^*(-5-4^*3)^2+1$
7040	12144	$1^*-2^*(-345-6-7+89A)^*-B$	$-B^*(-A+9)^*-8^*(-76-5-4-32-1)$
7041	12145	$1^*2+3^*(4^5-6^*-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+8-7^*6+(5^*4+3)^(2+1)$
7042	12146	$-1+234+5+(678+9A)^*B$	$B+A9^*87+6^*-54^*3^*(2-1)$
7043	12147	$-1-23-4^*5^*67-89^*-AB$	$-B+A^*(98+765)-4^*(-32+1)$
7044	12148	$-1+2-(-3-4^*(-56-78-9A)^*-B)$	$B+A98^*7+6^*-5+43^*21$
7045	12149	$(1^*2^3+4+5)^*6^*(7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A9^*87+6^*-54^*3+2+1$
7046	12150	$1^*-23^*(456-(789-A)+B)$	$-BA9-(8+7-6^*543^*(2+1))$
7047	12151	$1^*2+3^*4^*5^*(6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A9-8+7-65^*4^*(-32-1)$
7048	12152	$1-2^*(3-(4^5*6+7)+8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8)^*-7^*(6/(5+4^*3))^2-1$
7049	12153	$1+23^*-4^*-5+6789+AB$	$-B+A9^*8+(7-6543)^*(-2+1)$
704A	12154	$(-1+2-3^*(-4-5^*6)^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A^*987-(-6-54-3)^*-21$
704B	12155	$((-1+2^3)^*4+5+6+7+8)/9+A-B$	$-B^*(A9-876-5^*4-(-3-21))$
7050	12156	$-123+4+5^*-6+(-789-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-6^*5)^*(4^3+2)^2*1$
7051	12157	$-1-23+456-7+89A^*B$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^*(5+4^*3)^2-1$
7052	12158	$1-2^*-3456+7^*-8^*-9-A+B$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^*(5+4^*3)^2*1$
7053	12159	$1-(23-456+7+89^*-A^*B)$	$B+A+9-8+7^*6^*(-5^*4+3)^2-1$
7054	12160	$1+23+4^*56+78^*(9A+B)$	$B+A+9-8+7^*6^*(5+4^*3)^2*1$
7055	12161	$-12-34+567-8^*-9AB$	$-BA+98^*(76-5^*-4)-321$
7056	12162	$(1^*(-2^3-(4+5^*6))^*-7+8)/9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*(876+5-43^*-2)^*1$
7057	12163	$-12+34^*-5^*6+789A+B$	$BA-9+(8+7)^*(6+543+21)$
7058	12164	$-1-2^*((-3-4^5)^*6+7+8^*9)+A-B$	$-B-A9^*-8-(-7-(6543-2-1))$
7059	12165	$(1+2^*3)^*(4^5+6^*7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A+9-(8+7-6^*5^*((-4/3)^2+2+1))$
705A	12166	$-1+(-2^3+4^5-6^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B^*(A-98+7^*-65-4-321)$
705B	12167	$((1^2-3-4)^5/-6+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A9-(-8-7)-65^*4^*(-32-1)$
7060	12168	$1+23-(4-5)-(-6-(-789+A)^*-B)$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7^*6)^*(-5-4)^3-(2+1)$
7061	12169	$-1-(2+3)-(-4^*-5^*-67-89^*AB)$	$-B+A9^*8-(-7-6543)-2^*-1$
7062	12170	$-12+34+5+6-(789-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9-8-(7-6^*5)^(4-3+2)-1$
7063	12171	$-1-23-(-456-7+89^*A^*-B)$	$BA98+7-6^*(5+43)^*21$
7064	12172	$-1-2-34+567-8^*-9AB$	$B+A-(-987+6^*54^*(-3-21))$
7065	12173	$-1+2-3-4^*-5^*-67-89^*-AB$	$-BA9+8^*7+6^*-5^*(-4-321)$
7066	12174	$-123-4+567-89^*-A^*B$	$B-A^*(-98-765)+43^*(2+1)$
7067	12175	$-12-3+45+6+(-789+A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^*(5+4^*3)^2-1$
7068	12176	$1+23+4+5+6+(-789+A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^*(5^*4-3)^2*1$
7069	12177	$1-2^*34^*5-(-67-8-9)^*AB$	$B^*(-A9+8^*7+6+5-(-432+1))$
706A	12178	$1+2-(34-567)+8^*9AB$	$-B-A9^*-8-(-7-6543)+21$
706B	12179	$123-4-56^*-7+89A^*B$	$B+A9^*(8+7+65)-4^*3^*-21$
7070	12180	$-1^*(-2-34+5+6-7^*8)^*(9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7-6^*5)^*4^3*2-1$
7071	12181	$1-2-(3-456)-7-89^*-A^*B$	$-B-A^*-987-(-6^*5+4^*321)$
7072	12182	$-12-3+456+7+89^*A^*B$	$-B-A9-(87^*-6^*-5^*-4-32^*-1)$
7073	12183	$-1^*(2-3+4)^*(-5+67-89)^*AB$	$BA-9^*-87+6543-21$
7074	12184	$(-1+2-3)^*(-4^5*6+7^*8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7+6+(5^*4+3)^(2+1)$
7075	12185	$-1+2-(-34-5-6)-(-789+A)^*B$	$-B+A98-(-76+5)^*-4^*(3+21)$
7076	12186	$12-3+4^*5^*-67-89^*-AB$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6+5+4)^3-2^*1$
7077	12187	$123+4-56^*7^*(89-AB)$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6+5+4)^3-2+1$
7078	12188	$1-2+3+4+5^*6-78^*(-9A-B)$	$B^*(-A-9-8-(-765-43+2-1))$
7079	12189	$12-34+567-8^*-9AB$	$B+A+9^*8^*7+6^*5/4^*3^*2^2*1$
707A	12190	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^5*6-7^*8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8^*7+6^*5/4^*3^*2+1$
707B	12191	$1+2^*-3-456+(-7-89)^*-AB$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6+5+4)^3+2+1$
7080	12192	$12-3-4+5+(-67-8)^*(-9-AB)$	$-B+A9^*8+7+6543+21$
7081	12193	$1-23-(-4-567-8^*9AB)$	$-B-A^*(-98+7)+6543-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7082	12194	$-12*(345+67-8-9AB)$	$B+A+9*8+(7-6*5*4+3)^2+1$
7083	12195	$1+2-(3-(-4+56))-(-789+A)*-B$	$B+A+(9-8)^7+6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
7084	12196	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+(789-A)*B$	$B+A+9-8+7+(6+5+4*3)^(2+1)$
7085	12197	$-1+2+3-4-5+(-67-8)*(-9-AB)$	$-B+A98*-7+65*-4*3*-21$
7086	12198	$-1*(2-3)*456*(-7-89+AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+(6+5+4*3)^(2+1)$
7087	12199	$-123-4-(-5-6)*789+AB$	$B+A+9+8*(7*6+(-5+4)*3)^2+1$
7088	12200	$-1*2*(3-(-45+6))*(-78-9-A-B)$	$B+A*9*8-7+6543+21$
7089	12201	$-1+2+3-4*5*6*7-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9+8)*-7*6*((5*4-3)^2+1)$
708A	12202	$-12-(3-4)-(-567-8*9AB)$	$B+A+9-8+7+6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
708B	12203	$1+2+3-4*5*-6*7+89*AB$	$B+A+9/(8-7)+6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
7090	12204	$1*-2*(3*-4+56)*(-7-89+A-B)$	$B+A+9+8-7+6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
7091	12205	$-1-2-3-4+567+8*9AB$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6*5)^(4-3+2)*1$
7092	12206	$12-34-(-5-6)*(789+A-B)$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6*5)^(4-3+2)+1$
7093	12207	$-1+2+3+4+56+(-789+A)*-B$	$BA-9*-87-(-6543+2-1)$
7094	12208	$-12+3+4+567+8*9AB$	$BA9+876+5432-1$
7095	12209	$-12+3*456*7-89A+B$	$BA9+876-5432*-1$
7096	12210	$1-234*-56-7+8*9*-AB$	$BA9+876-(-5432-1)$
7097	12211	$-1+2*(34-56*-78)+9-A-B$	$-B-A9+87*6*5*4*3*(2+1)$
7098	12212	$-1+2*(3-4)+567+8*9AB$	$BA*(98-(76-54)-(3-(-2+1)))$
7099	12213	$1+23-(-456+7)-89*A*-B$	$B+A-9-8+7*6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
709A	12214	$1+2*-3-(-4-567)-8*-9AB$	$-B+A9+8*-7*6*(-54+3+21)$
709B	12215	$12+3*456*7-(89A+B)$	$B+A+(-9+(-8*7*-6+5)*4)*3^2-1$
70A0	12216	$1+2345-67*-89-A-B$	$B+A+9*(8*7*6-5+4)^(3+2)^(1)$
70A1	12217	$1+2+3-4+567+8*9AB$	$B+A+9*(8*7*6-5+4)^(3+2)+1$
70A2	12218	$1+2+3*4^(5-6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$-BA-9*8+(-7-65)*4*(-32+1)$
70A3	12219	$-123-4*5*-6*7+89A*B$	$BA9+87*-6*(5*4-32+1)$
70A4	12220	$-1-(-2*-3-4*(5-6*-7*8))*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+(8+7-(6-5*4))^3)*2^2-1$
70A5	12221	$-123-45-(-6+78+9)*-AB$	$B*(A98+7+6-5+4-321)$
70A6	12222	$-12*(34-567+8+9-AB)$	$B+A-(-9/((8+7)*(-6-5)^(4+3)*2)^(1)-1$
70A7	12223	$1+2+3-4+56+(-789+A)*-B$	$-BA+9-87*6*5*4*3-(2-1)$
70A8	12224	$1-(2-34-5)-(-67+8)*(-9-AB)$	$B+A-9*8*(-7-6*5*4)*3/2-1$
70A9	12225	$1+2+3-(-4-567)-8*-9AB$	$-B-A+98*7*6+5+4321$
70AA	12226	$123+4*-567+89AB$	$B-A*9*-8*(7-6)*(-5*-4-3)-21$
70AB	12227	$-1*(-2*(-3+4^5)*6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7+6+(-5-4)^(3-2)^(1)$
70B0	12228	$1+2-(-34-5)-(-67+8)*(-9-AB)$	$B+A-9*(8+(7+6-5)^(4/-3-(-2+1)))$
70B1	12229	$-123+45-6+(789+A)*B$	$BA-9+8*-7*6*(-54+3+21)$
70B2	12230	$12-3+4+567-8*-9AB$	$-BA9-8*-76*5*-4-321$
70B3	12231	$-1-2*3-(456-78*(9+AB))$	$B+A+9*8+7*6*(5+4*3)^2+1$
70B4	12232	$-1*2*(345+67+8*(9-A))*-B$	$B*(-A+9*8+765+4-32-1)$
70B5	12233	$-1-(23-(-45-6)-(7+89))*-A*-B$	$BA+9*8+765+4+321$
70B6	12234	$-1+2345-67*-89-(-A+B)$	$B+A-9*8+(7+6-5)^(4*3-2-1)$
70B7	12235	$-1*(-2345+67*-89-A+B)$	$-B+A-98*-7*6-5+4321$
70B8	12236	$12+3+4-(-567-8*9AB)$	$B+A*(-9-8)*-76+5*(-432-1)$
70B9	12237	$-1+2+3-4+567+8*9AB$	$B-(A+98*-7*6+5-4321)$
70BA	12238	$1-(-2345+67*-89+A-B)$	$B+A-9*8+(7+6-5)^(4*3+2-1)$
70BB	12239	$1+2345+6+78*9*A+B$	$-B+A*(9+876-54+32*1)$
7100	12240	$1-2*(3-45)+6+(789-A)*B$	$B+A-9*8+(7+6-5)^(4*3+2+1)$
7101	12241	$-12+3+4+567+8*9AB$	$B-A*(-9-876)-5*43-21$
7102	12242	$-1+234+5*(678+9AB)$	$-B-A+98*76-5-4*3-21$
7103	12243	$1^2+3-(-4^5-6*7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*((8-7*-6+5)*4-3*2)^(1)$
7104	12244	$-1+2*-3-4*-5*6*(78+9)+AB$	$B-A98*7+(-654+3)*-21$
7105	12245	$-1-234*5+(6-(7+89))*-AB$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)/(-6^5-5-4)^(3^2-1)$
7106	12246	$1*(23-45)*6*(678-9AB)$	$B+A-9*(8+(7+6-5)^(4/-3-2+1))$
7107	12247	$-123+4-5-(-6-789-A)*B$	$B+A+9+8+7*6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
7108	12248	$-1-(-2+3+4+56-(789+A)*B)$	$-B-A-9-8+(7+6-5)^(4*3-2)^(1)$
7109	12249	$12-3-(456-78*(9+AB))$	$B+A+(9-8-(7+6))*5(4^3+2)^(1)$
710A	12250	$12*(-345-(-67-89A-B))$	$-B-A*(-9-87)-(-6543-2)*1$
710B	12251	$1+2-3+4+5-((-6-7)*8*9A-B)$	$B-A*(-9-8)*(-7+65+4-3+2-1)$
7110	12252	$-1-(2-34-567)+8*9AB$	$B+A98-(-7*6*5*-43+21)$
7111	12253	$-1-2*(3+4)*5(5+6*78)*(9-A)*B$	$-B+A98-7*6*5*4+3+2*-1$
7112	12254	$-1-2*(345-6*(789-A))-B$	$B*(A-(9+8*-76)-(-54-321))$
7113	12255	$12+3-456+78*(9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8*(7-6-5)^(4))*-3*-2*1$
7114	12256	$-1+2+3+4-(-567-8*9AB)$	$-B-A98-7-6*5*(-4-321)$
7115	12257	$1-23-4-56-(-789-A)*B$	$-B-A-9+8*(7-6-5)^(4*3*2-1)$
7116	12258	$1-(-2-(34+567)-8*9AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+(-7-6+5)^(4)^(3/2-1))$
7117	12259	$1-2*(3-4^5)*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A*9+8*7*6*5*4*(3-2)*1$
7118	12260	$-1-(-2*(-3+4^5)*6+7)+8+9+A-B$	$B+A9*(8+76)+54-321$
7119	12261	$-1+23+4+56+78*(9A+B)$	$B-A*(-9-876+54-32*1)$
711A	12262	$-1-2*(3-4^5*-6*(7-8)+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7*6+5)*-4*3^2+1$
711B	12263	$-12-3*45*6-(-78-9)*AB$	$BA+98-7-65*4*(-32-1)$
7120	12264	$12*(-34-56+789-AB)$	$B+A-9*(8+(7+6-5)^(4/-3-(2+1)))$
7121	12265	$1+2*((-3+4^5)*6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$-B*(A-(98+765-43)+21)$
7122	12266	$-1-23-45-6+(-789-A)*-B$	$-B-A98*-7+654+321$
7123	12267	$12-3-4*5*6*-7+8*9AB$	$-B+A98*7-65*(4+3-21)$
7124	12268	$-1*2+3*4^(5-6+7)-8-9+A-B$	$B-A+9-87*(-65-4-32)+1$
7125	12269	$12-(-34-567-8*9AB)$	$B+A-9*8+(7*6+5+4)^(3)^(2-1)$
7126	12270	$1^2+3*4^(5-6+7)-8-9+A-B$	$-B-A*-98+7+6543-21$
7127	12271	$1^2+3*4^(5-6+7)-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9*8+(7*6+5+4)^(3)^(2+1)$
7128	12272	$-1*2*(34-567-8*(9A+B))$	$B+A+9*8*7/6+(5*4+3)^(2+1)$
7129	12273	$1+2+3*4^(5-6+7)-8-9+A-B$	$-BA-9-8+(-7-65)*4*(-32+1)$
712A	12274	$1+2+3+4+(5+6)*789+A+B$	$B+A-9-((8-(7+6-5)^(4))^(3+2)^(1))$
712B	12275	$1-2*(3-4^5*6)+7/(8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*(-7-6)*(-5+4)^(3))^(2)^(1)$
7130	12276	$-1*(-234-567-8+9A)*B$	$B*(-A+9+8+765-4+3+21)$
7131	12277	$-12-34*(-5+67)+89AB$	$B+A-9+(-8+(-7-(6-5)^(4))^(3+2-1))$
7132	12278	$-12*(3-45-(678-9A)+B)$	$B+A-9+(-8+(7+6-5)^(4))^(3+2/1)$
7133	12279	$1^2+3-4*(-5+6*-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A98+7*-6*5*-43-2*-1$
7134	12280	$1*2+3-4*(-5-6*7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B-A9-876*-5*(4-3*2)*-1$
7135	12281	$-1-2-(3-(4-5-67))*(-8-9-AB)$	$B+A+9*((-8-7)*6*-5+4)*3+2^(1)$
7136	12282	$-1*-2*(3+4^5*6+7-8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9*((-8-7)*6*-5+4)*3+2+1$
7137	12283	$-1-2+3*-4+5(6-78-9)*-AB$	$B+A+(-9+8^((7-6)^(5*4)))^(3+2-1)$
7138	12284	$-123+45*(6-7+89+AB)$	$BA98+76*(-54-(3+21))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7139	12285	$1-2+3^4(5-6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^((7-6)^5))^3+2+1$
713A	12286	$1+23-(-4+56)-(7+89)^*-A^*B$	$B+A+(-9-8^((7-6)^5))^*-4^*-3^*2+1$
713B	12287	$1234+567-8^*9^*-AB$	$-BA-9^*(-876-54+3^*-21)$
7140	12288	$-1-2-34^*(-5+67)+89AB$	$B+A98^*7-(-654-321)$
7141	12289	$1+2+3^4(5-6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2-1$
7142	12290	$1-2-34^*(-5+67)+89AB$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2^1$
7143	12291	$1+2+3^4(5-6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2+1$
7144	12292	$1+2^*(3+4^5*6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*((7-(6+5))^4^*-3^*2+1)$
7145	12293	$1-2+34+(5+6+789-A)^*B$	$-BA9-8-7^*-65^*(43-21)$
7146	12294	$1-(-2-34^*(5-67)-89AB)$	$-B+A^*9^*-8+7654-(-3+2)^*1$
7147	12295	$-12-(34-567)+89^*A^*B$	$B-A^*(-9-87)-(-6543-21)$
7148	12296	$-1+23-(-4-5+(-6-7)^*-8^*-9A)-B$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^2-1$
7149	12297	$1+2^*3^4(5+6-7)^*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A^*98+7^*(6543+2)^*-1$
714A	12298	$-1^*(-23-(-4-56))^*(-78+9A)^*-B$	$-B^*(A9-87)^*(-6-5-(4+3+2+1))$
714B	12299	$-1-2-(34+5+6)-(-789-A)^*B$	$-B+A987+6+5^*43^*-21$
7150	12300	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^5*6+7-8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*(7-6-5)^4^*3^*2^*1$
7151	12301	$-123+45+(-67+89^*-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9+8^*(7-6-5)^4^*3^*2+1$
7152	12302	$-1^*2+3^4(5-6+7)+8+9+A-B$	$B-A^*-98-7-(-6543-(-2+1))$
7153	12303	$1-2+3^4(5-6+7)+8+9+A-B$	$B-A^*(9-876)-5+4-32+1$
7154	12304	$1^*2^*(345-67^*-8^*9-A-B)$	$B+A^*98-(-7-6543-2+1)$
7155	12305	$12+34^*(5-67)+89AB$	$B+A^*(-9+876)-5+4+3+21$
7156	12306	$-1-2-34+567-89^*-A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8-7-6)^5^*4^*3-2-1$
7157	12307	$1+2^*(3+4^5*6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$B-A^*-98^*-7+654^*(-3+2+1)$
7158	12308	$12+3+4-56+(789+A)^*B$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2^*1$
7159	12309	$-1234-5^*-67+89A^*B$	$-BA-98-(-7654+321)$
715A	12310	$-1-(-2^3-4^5-6^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-A^*98+7654+321$
715B	12311	$1-(2+34)+5-6-(-789-A)^*B$	$-B-A9^*-87-(654+32-1)$
7160	12312	$1^*-2^3-4^*(56-(78-9-AB))$	$-BA-9876+54^*321$
7161	12313	$1-23^*-4+5+(6+789-A)^*B$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6-5)^4^*3+2+1$
7162	12314	$-1+2345-67^*(-89+A-B)$	$B+A+(9-8+(7+6-5)^4)^*3+2/1$
7163	12315	$123-4^*(56+78+9A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6-5-4)^*3-2-1$
7164	12316	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^5)^*6+7^*8+9+A-B$	$B+A^*-9^*8-(-7654-3)+2^*-1$
7165	12317	$-1-(23+4-567-89^*A^*B)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6-5)^4^*3^*2-1$
7166	12318	$12345-6-(-789-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(7-6-5)^4^*3^*2^*1$
7167	12319	$-1+2^*345+6789-AB$	$-B+A^*(98+765+4+3+2+1)$
7168	12320	$-12^*(-3+456-78-9AB)$	$B^*(A-9-8)^*(-7-65-43-21)$
7169	12321	$1+2^*345-(-6789+AB)$	$B+A987+6-5^*-43^*-21$
716A	12322	$1-(-23-(-45-6)-(789+A)^*B)$	$BA+98^*(76+5-(-4-3-2)+1)$
716B	12323	$12-34+567-89^*A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2-1$
7170	12324	$-1^*-2^*3^*(456-7-(8-9AB))$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2^*1$
7171	12325	$12-3-(-45+6^*7+89)^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4^*3-2+1$
7172	12326	$1234-5^*-67^*(-89+AB)$	$BA-98-7-6^*-543^*(2+1)$
7173	12327	$1^*2-3^*45^*-67-89-AB$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4^*3+2-1$
7174	12328	$-1+234^*-5+6-7+89A^*B$	$B+A^*98-7-(-6543-21)$
7175	12329	$-1-2^*-3^*45-(6^*7-89^*-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6-5)^4^*3+2+1$
7176	12330	$1+2^*(-3+4^5-6^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6+5)^*(4^*(3+2)+1)$
7177	12331	$-1^*(234-5^*6+7+8)^*(9+A)^*B$	$B^*(A+9)^*(8+7+65-(-4+32)+1)$
7178	12332	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^5*6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*(8-7+65+321)$
7179	12333	$1+2-(-3-(-4+5+6))-(-7-89)^*A^*B$	$BA-987+6^*5^*(-4+321)$
717A	12334	$-12-345^*6+7+89AB$	$B+A-9^*(8+(-7-6-5+4)^3)/2+1$
717B	12335	$-12-345^*-6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$B+A+9^*(8+(7+6-5)^4)/3+2^*1$
7180	12336	$1234^*(5-(-6-7-8+9-A+B))$	$B+A+(9+8^((7-6)^5*5-4+3))^*(2+1)$
7181	12337	$-123-45^*(6-7)^*(89+AB)$	$-BA-987+6^*543^*(2+1)$
7182	12338	$(-1-2^*(3+4^5))^*6/(7-8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*(7+6-5-4))^*-3+2^1$
7183	12339	$-1+234-56^*-7^*(-89+AB)$	$B+A+9+(8+(-7-6+5)^4)^*3-(2+1)$
7184	12340	$1-23-(-45-(67-89^*-A)^*B)$	$B+A-9+8+(7^*6+5+4^3)^2-1$
7185	12341	$1+234+56^*7^*(-89+AB)$	$B+A+(9-8-7+6^*5^*4-3)^2-1$
7186	12342	$-1^*2^*(3^*4+567^*-8+(9+A)^*B)$	$-B^*(-A-9+8-(765+43-21))$
7187	12343	$1-2+3^45^*67-8+(-9-A)^*B$	$B+A+(9-8-7+6^*5^*4-3)^2+1$
7188	12344	$1+2^*(3-(-4^5*6-7-8-9))-(-A-B)$	$BA9-8+(7-65)^*-4^*32-1$
7189	12345	$12-34^*(56+7)+89AB$	$-B+A98-76^*-5^*4^*-3^*-2^*1$
718A	12346	$-1^*(-2345-67^*89-A^*B)$	$-B+A-(9+87^*6^*-5^*4+3+2-1)$
718B	12347	$1-2-345^*6+7+89AB$	$-B-A9^*-87-654-3+2^*1$
7190	12348	$12-345^*6-7+89AB$	$-B-A9^*-87+654^*(3-2)^*-1$
7191	12349	$1^*(-2-3+4)^*(-567+89^*A^*-B)$	$-B-A^*(9-(8+765-4^*-32^*1))$
7192	12350	$-1^*(23-45)^*(6^*(78+9)-AB)$	$B+A+9^*(8-7+(6^*5+4+3)^2)-1$
7193	12351	$-1-(-2+3)-(-4-567)-89^*-A^*B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^2-1$
7194	12352	$1-2^*(-3-4^5*6+7)+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^2^*1$
7195	12353	$-1-2-(-3-4-567+89^*A^*-B)$	$-B^*(-A-987+6+5^*43+21)$
7196	12354	$-1^*-2^*((-3+4^5)^*6+7^*8)-9+A-B$	$-BA^*(-98-7+6-5-4-(-32-1))$
7197	12355	$12+3-(-4+56)^*(-78-9A+B)$	$-B-A+9^*8^*7+6^*5+4^3(3^*2^*1)$
7198	12356	$123+456-7-89^*-A^*B$	$-B-A+9^*8^*7+6^*5+4^3(3^*2)+1$
7199	12357	$1+234^*56+78^*(-9^*A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-(-8-7)+6)^*(5-(-4^*(3+2)+1))$
719A	12358	$1-2+3^4(5-6+7)+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7^*6+5+4^3)^2-1$
719B	12359	$1+2+3+4+567-89^*-A^*B$	$B-A^*(-9-876-5^*-4)-32^*-1$
71A0	12360	$-1+2-3^*-4^*-5+(-6-789-A)^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7^*6+5+4^3)^2+1$
71A1	12361	$12-(-345+6-78^*(9A+B))$	$B+A+(9+8+(7+6-5)^4)^*3+2-1$
71A2	12362	$-12^*(3-4)^*(567+89-A-B)$	$BA9-87-6^*-54^*(3+21)$
71A3	12363	$1+2^*((3+4^5)^*6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+(7+6-5)^4)^*3+2+1$
71A4	12364	$1-23-4^*-5^*-6+7+89A^*B$	$-B-A+9-8^*(-7-6)^*((-5+4^3)^2+1)$
71A5	12365	$-1-23^*4-(-5-6-789-A)^*B$	$B+A9^*87-654-3-2^*1$
71A6	12366	$-1+2345+67^*89+AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(-7^*6+(-5-4)^3)^*-2^*1$
71A7	12367	$-1^*(-2345-67^*89-AB)$	$B+A98-76^*-5^*-4-(-3-21)$
71A8	12368	$1+2345+67^*89+AB$	$B+A-9+8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^2^*1$
71A9	12369	$123-456^*(7+89-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^2-1$
71AA	12370	$123+456+7-89^*A^*-B$	$B-A9^*-87-654-3+2+1$
71AB	12371	$123-4^*-5+(6+7+8)^*(9+AB)$	$B+A^*(98+765-4+32+1)$
71B0	12372	$1^*2^*-3^*-4-(567+89A-B)$	$B+A9^*87-654-(-3+2-1)$
71B1	12373	$12-(-345-6)+78^*(9A+B)$	$B+A9^*87-654-3^*(-2+1)$
71B2	12374	$-1-2-(3^*-45^*6-7)+8^*9AB$	$B-A+98-7^*(65+4^*-321)$
71B3	12375	$-12-(-34-567)+89^*-A^*-B$	$-B^*(-A98-76-(-54-321))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
71B4	12376	$12^*(-3+45+678+9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8-7^*-6^*5)/4^{\wedge}3+2+1$
71B5	12377	$12+3+4^*5^*-6^*(-7-8^*(-9+A+B))$	$B+A+9+8+7^*((6^*-5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
71B6	12378	$-1+2^*-345-6-(-789A+B)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3-2-1$
71B7	12379	$-1-2+34^*5-(-67-8)^*(9+AB)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3-2^*1$
71B8	12380	$-1-2^*((-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6+7)+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3-2+1$
71B9	12381	$(-1+2-3)^*(-4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B-A^*(9-876)-(-5+4-32-1)$
71BA	12382	$123-4+567+8^*9AB$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3+2-1$
71BB	12383	$1^*2/(3^{\wedge}4+5)^{\wedge}(6-7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3+2^*1$
7200	12384	$1^*(23-(-45-6))^*(7-(-8-9A-B))$	$B+A+9^*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3+2+1$
7201	12385	$-1+2^*(-345-6^*789^*(A-B))$	$-B+A9^*87-(654-32+1)$
7202	12386	$1^*-2^*(345-6^*789)^*(-A+B)$	$-B^*(A9-(876-5)-(-4-3+21))$
7203	12387	$-12-3^*45^*6-(-789A+B)$	$-B+A9^*87-(654-32-1)$
7204	12388	$12-34-5+(-67-89^*A)^*B$	$B+A9^*(8+76)+5^*(-43+2^*-1)$
7205	12389	$-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6+7^*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8+7^*6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3/2-1$
7206	12390	$1^*(2+34)^*(56-7+89+AB)$	$B+A+9^*(8+((7+6-5)^{\wedge}4+3)/(2+1))$
7207	12391	$1234-56+7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$-B-A+(9+8)^*(7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
7208	12392	$1+2-345-6+78^*(9+AB)$	$B-A9^*-87-654-3+2+1$
7209	12393	$-1^*-23^*(-4-5)^*(67-8-(-9+AB))$	$-BA+987+6543-2-1$
720A	12394	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-BA+987+6543+2^*-1$
720B	12395	$-1+2^*3+4^*5^*-67-89A^*-B$	$-BA-(-987-6543+2-1)$
7210	12396	$-1234-(567-89AB)$	$-BA+987+6543^*(2-1)$
7211	12397	$1+2-(3-4^*56)-(-789+A)^*B$	$-BA+987-(-6543-2)-1$
7212	12398	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3^*-4)^*(-5+6^*-7)^*8-9+A-B$	$-BA+987+6543+2^*1$
7213	12399	$-12+3^*45^*67-8-(-9+AB)$	$-BA+987+6543+2+1$
7214	12400	$1^*2^*-34^*-5^*(-6-78+9A+B)$	$-BA9+8+765^*(4+3^*(2+1))$
7215	12401	$-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6+7+8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8+7^*)(6-5^{\wedge}4)/(3/2-1)$
7216	12402	$-1^*-2^*-3^*45^*(6^*(7-8-9)+A+B)$	$-B-A-9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
7217	12403	$1234-(-5-6^*-7-8^*-9A^*-B)$	$-B^*-A+(9-8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4)^*3+2/1$
7218	12404	$1+23^*-45+67+89^*AB$	$-B-A9^*(-87+6)-(-5-43^*-2+1)$
7219	12405	$-1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^*8)+9-(-A-B)$	$B+A+98^*76-5+4^*321$
721A	12406	$-12-3+4+56-(-789-A)^*B$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7-6)^*((-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
721B	12407	$12+3-4^*5^*67+89A^*B$	$B-A9^*-87-654-(-32+1)$
7220	12408	$-1^*2^*-3^*(456+7-8+9AB)$	$-BA-9-(8-7654+321)$
7221	12409	$-12+3456+7^*-8^*-9A-B$	$-B-A+9+(-8-7)^*6^*(-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1$
7222	12410	$1+234^*-5+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A^*987-(-6^*5^*(-43-2)+1)$
7223	12411	$-1-(-2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5^*6)-7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8)^{\wedge}(7-6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
7224	12412	$1^*2^*(34-5-6)^*(78-9+AB)$	$B-A-9^*(-87-6+5+43^*-21)$
7225	12413	$-1-(-2345+678^*-9+AB)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7226	12414	$-1+2+3^*45^*67-8-(-9+AB)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
7227	12415	$1+2345-678^*-9-AB$	$BA9-8-7^*-6^*-5^*43^*(2-1)$
7228	12416	$-1-2-3^*4^*-5+6-(-789-A)^*B$	$B+A+(9+8)^{\wedge}(7-6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}1$
7229	12417	$1234-5^*6+7+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+(9+8)^{\wedge}(7-6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1$
722A	12418	$-1^*(2+3^*45^*-67-8^*(-9-A)-B)$	$BA9-8+7^*6^*5^*43+2+1$
722B	12419	$1-2-3^*-4^*(567+89+AB)$	$-B-A9-8+7654-321$
7230	12420	$-1^*-2^*3^*(456-(7-8-9AB))$	$-B-A+9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
7231	12421	$1^*2+(3^{\wedge}4+5+6)^*(7+8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+987+6543+2+1$
7232	12422	$1-(-23-4)+5^*-6^*7^*(8^*9-AB)$	$B-A9-(8+7)^*(6+5)^*(-43-21)$
7233	12423	$1-2+3^*-45^*-67-8-9A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8+7^*6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3^*2^{\wedge}-1$
7234	12424	$(-1^*-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^{\wedge}5/-6+7+8)^*9-(-A-B)$	$-BA-(9-8-7654+321)$
7235	12425	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}3^*4+5))^*(6^*7^*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A^*987-(6+543)^*-2^*-1$
7236	12426	$1+2-3^*-45^*-6-(-789A-B)$	$-BA+9-8+7654-321$
7237	12427	$-1+2-(-34-56)-(-7-89)^*A^*B$	$B+A^*(-9+876)+54-3+2+1$
7238	12428	$(1+2)^*((-3-4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^*-8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*(6-5)^*-4^*3^*2-1$
7239	12429	$-1-2^*-345+6789-A-B$	$-B-A98^*-7+6-543^*2^*-1$
723A	12430	$-1+(-2-(3+4^{\wedge}5/-6-7))^*-8^*-9+A-B$	$-B-A-98+7654-321$
723B	12431	$1-2^*-345-(-6789-(-A-B))$	$B+A-(9+8-76)^*5^*(-4+32)^*1$
7240	12432	$1^*(23+45+678)^*(-9+A+B)$	$BA9+8+7^*(-6+543)^*2+1$
7241	12433	$1+2^*34+5-6-(789+A)^*B$	$-B-(A+9876+54^*-321)$
7242	12434	$-1+2345-(-678^*9-A^*-B)$	$BA9-876^*(-5-4)-321$
7243	12435	$1+2-(-345-6-78-9)^*(A+B)$	$-B-(A9-8-7654)-321$
7244	12436	$-12+3^*-45^*-67-(-8+9+A^*B)$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5+4)/(3+2^{\wedge}1)$
7245	12437	$12+34-5^*-6+(789+A)^*B$	$-B-A^*-987+6^*(-5^*43-2)^*1$
7246	12438	$-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B+A9^*-8-(-7654-321)$
7247	12439	$-1+234+(-5-6)^*-789-AB$	$-BA9-8^*7-6^*-54^*(32-1)$
7248	12440	$-1-2^*(3-(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7)-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8+7^*(6^*5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7249	12441	$1^*(23-4-5^*6^*7+8^*-9A)^*B$	$B-A9-8-(-7654+321)$
724A	12442	$-1-2+3456-7^*-8^*9A+B$	$-BA+9+8+7654-321$
724B	12443	$-123-45^*(-6-78-9-AB)$	$-B-A-9-(8-7-6)^{\wedge}5^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
7250	12444	$(-1^*-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^{\wedge}5/-6+7+8)^*9+A+B$	$B+A-9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
7251	12445	$1-2^*((-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6-7^*8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A+(9+8+(-7-6^{\wedge}5)^*4)/(-3/2-1)$
7252	12446	$-123+4^*56+(-789-A)^*B$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7-(6^{\wedge}5+4))^*3/2-1$
7253	12447	$-1^*-23^*(-4^*(5+6)-7^*8^*-9-A+B)$	$B+A+(9-8+7^*6)^*(5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7254	12448	$1-2+3-4+5+(6-78-9)^*AB$	$B+A+(9-(8-7^*6))^*(5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
7255	12449	$1+2+3^*45^*67-(8+9A)+B$	$-B-A^*-987+(6-543)^*2^*1$
7256	12450	$-1-2^*-345-6789^*(A-B)$	$-B+A-98+7654-321$
7257	12451	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5^*6+7+8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8-7)^*6^*(-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1$
7258	12452	$-1+2^*(-3-4)^*56-(-789A-B)$	$B-A-(98-7654+321)$
7259	12453	$-1+23^*(-45-6)-(-7-89A)^*B$	$-B+A-(9876+54^*-321)$
725A	12454	$123-4-56+(789+A)^*B$	$B+A9^*(87+6-(5+4))-321$
725B	12455	$(-1^*-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*-5+6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B-A-9876-54^*-321$
7260	12456	$-1^*2^*-3^*(-4+567+89A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5-4))/(-3-2^*1)$
7261	12457	$-1+2^*(-3-456)-7-89^*-AB$	$B-A9+8+7654-321$
7262	12458	$1-23^*-4+567+89^*-A^*-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)^*(-7-6^*-5^*-4^*3)^*2+1$
7263	12459	$12+3456+7^*-8^*-9A+B$	$-B+A^*-98^*7+(-6+54)^*3^*2+1$
7264	12460	$-12^*(-3-(45-(-678-9+AB)))$	$B+A9^*-8+7654+321$
7265	12461	$-1-(23-4-56^*-7^*(-8-9-A))^*B$	$B+A9-87^*-6^*5^*4-32-1$
7266	12462	$1/(2-3)-4^*(-5^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
7267	12463	$-12+3^*-45^*-67-89+A+B$	$B^*(A+9^*(-87-(65-43-2)))^*-1$
7268	12464	$-1^*-234^*(-5+6-78+9A+B)$	$BA98-76^*-5^*(4-(-3+21))$
7269	12465	$1-234^*(5-(6-78)-(9A+B))$	$B+A+(9-8-7-6^{\wedge}5^*4)/(-3/2-1)$
726A	12466	$-1+2-3^*-45^*67+8^*(9-A-B)$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
726B	12467	$((1+2)^3 \wedge 3 - 4^5) / (-6+7) * 8^9 + A - B$	$B + A + (9+8+(-7-6^5)^4) / (-3/2-1)$
7270	12468	$12+3*4*(-56+789)+A*B$	$B+A+9*(8+7+(-6^5-4-3)^2-1)$
7271	12469	$(-1+2^3)*(-4-5*(6-7*8^9))+A-B$	$B-A98+7*65*(43-21)$
7272	12470	$-1+2*(3+45)+6+(-789-A)*-B$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6^5)^4/(3/2+1)$
7273	12471	$-1+2*345+6789+A+B$	$B-A*(-987+65+43+21)$
7274	12472	$1+2-3-(-45+(-6-789-A)*B)$	$B+A-98+7654-321$
7275	12473	$1-2*-345+6789-(-A-B)$	$BA+9-87*-6*-5*-4-32*1$
7276	12474	$12*(3-45+67-(-8+9A))*-B$	$B*(-A9+876-5-(-43+21))$
7277	12475	$1+2+3*(4^5 \wedge 6 / (7+8)-9)+A-B$	$-B-A9*(-87+6)-54+32-1$
7278	12476	$-1+(-2+3/(4-5))^6+7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8+7+(6^5+4+3)^2)-1$
7279	12477	$1234-5-6*-7-8*-9A*B$	$-B-A9*(-87-(6-5)-(-4-3))-21$
727A	12478	$-123-4*-5*(-67+8)*-9-AB$	$B+A+9*(8+7+(6^5+4+3)^2)+1$
727B	12479	$1234-5-6*7*(8-9-AB)$	$B+A-((9+(8-(7+6))^5)^4-3*-2^1)$
7280	12480	$-1*-2*3*-4*(56+7-8)*(-9-A+B)$	$BA9+8+7+6*-54*(-3-21)$
7281	12481	$1+2*-345*(-6-7)-8+9-AB$	$-B-A9*(-87+6)+5-43+21$
7282	12482	$-1-23+456+78*(9A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8*(7+6^5+4))/(3+2^1)$
7283	12483	$1*-23-(-456-78*(9A+B))$	$B+A+(9+8*(7+6^5+4))/(3+2)+1$
7284	12484	$-1-2-3+4*5*(6+7-8)-9+A-B$	$B-A*(-9-876)+5-4+32*-1$
7285	12485	$-1-234-56+78*(9A+B)$	$-B*(-A-98-765+43+21)$
7286	12486	$1-2-3+4*5*(6+7-8)-9+A-B$	$-B+A9+8*(765+4+321)$
7287	12487	$1234+5*6+(7+8*9A)*B$	$-B-A+9-(8-7-6)^5*4-3+2/1$
7288	12488	$12+3*45*67-8-9*A+B$	$B+A+(9+(8-7-6)^5)^*-4+3*(2-1)$
7289	12489	$1234+5+6*7*(-8+9+AB)$	$-BA-9*-87-65*-4*-32*-1$
728A	12490	$-1+234*5+6+78*9A-B$	$B+A+(9+(8-(7+6))^5)^*-4+3+2/1$
728B	12491	$12-3*-45*67-(89-A-B)$	$B+A+(9-8+7*6)*((5+4*3)^2+1)$
7290	12492	$-1-23-(45*6+(7-89)*AB)$	$-B-A+987+6543-21$
7291	12493	$1+23-4*-5+(-6+78+9)*AB$	$-B-A+9-(8-7-6)^5*4+3+2/1$
7292	12494	$1^2+3+4*5*(6+7-8)-9+A-B$	$-BA9-8+7+6*5*4*(32-1)$
7293	12495	$-1+2*(-345+6*789)+A*B$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7)+6^5/4)^*-3*-2*1$
7294	12496	$-1+2345+6*(7-(8-9AB))$	$B*(-A9+876+5-4-3+21)$
7295	12497	$-12+3*-45*-6+7+89*A*B$	$-BA-9*-8-(-765+4+321)$
7296	12498	$-1234+567+89*AB$	$-B-A9*-87-(6+5+4+3)+21$
7297	12499	$-12-(-3-456)-78*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A*-9*(-87-(-6+5+4+3)+21)$
7298	12500	$-1+2*3456-78*-9+A+B$	$B+A9+87*(6+5-43)*(-2-1)$
7299	12501	$-123-4*56*(78-9-AB)$	$-B-A98*-7-6*5*(-43-2-1)$
729A	12502	$1+2*-34+5+(-67-(8+9))*-AB$	$-B+A*(-9+876)-(-5+4+3)*(2+1)$
729B	12503	$-1-2*3*-4*(-5*-67-(-89-A-B))$	$-B-A*(-9-876-5+4)+3*2*-1$
72A0	12504	$1*-2*3*(-456-(7+8)-9AB)$	$B+A-9+(-8+7+6)^5*4-3^2+1$
72A1	12505	$1+2+3+4*5*(6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$BA9-8-76*-5*4*3*-2*-1$
72A2	12506	$-12-3-45-(67-(-8-9))*-AB$	$B+A-9-(8-7-6)^5*4-3*2*1$
72A3	12507	$1*2-3+4*5*(6+7-8)+9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-(8+7))*(6-5*-43)*-2*1$
72A4	12508	$1+2*-3*4*-56*7-8+9AB$	$-B+A9*87+6-(543+2)-1$
72A5	12509	$1234+56-7+8*-9A*-B$	$-B+A9*87+6-543-2*1$
72A6	12510	$1*2*-3*(4-(567-8-9A*-B))$	$-BA9+8+7-6*-54*(32-1)$
72A7	12511	$1+2+3*4*5*(6/(7+8)+9+A-B)$	$B+A*(9+876-5+4)+3-2-1$
72A8	12512	$1-2+3+456-78*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A+987+6543-21$
72A9	12513	$1*2+3+4*5*(6+7-8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-(8-7-6)^5*4+3-2^1$
72AA	12514	$-1+2+3+456+78*(9A+B)$	$B-A-(-987-6543+21)$
72AB	12515	$1+2*3+4*5*(6+7-8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A-98*-7-65*-4*-32*-1$
72B0	12516	$123-4-(-567-89*A*B)$	$-B-A+987-(-6543+2-1)$
72B1	12517	$123-(-456+7*8*(9+A))*-B$	$-B+A9+87*-6*5*-4+3+2+1$
72B2	12518	$-1-2*(3-4^5*6-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$-B-A+987+6543+2-1$
72B3	12519	$(1+(2+3)^4)*(-5*-6+7-8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A+987+6543+2*1$
72B4	12520	$-1/((-2-3)/4)*(5^6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B-A+987+6543+2+1$
72B5	12521	$-1*-2*((-3+4^5)^6-(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$-BA-9*(-8-(7+6))*(-5+4-3)*(-2+1)$
72B6	12522	$-1*2^3+4*5*(6+7-8)+9+A+B$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6)^5*4-3^2+1$
72B7	12523	$1234+56+7-8*9A*-B$	$B+A+9-(8-7-6)^5*4-3*2-1$
72B8	12524	$123+4-(-567-89*A*B)$	$-B+A9*87-6-543+21$
72B9	12525	$(-1+2-3)*(-4^5*6-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$-B+A98+76*(54-3)*-2*-1$
72BA	12526	$1*-2*(3-4)*(567*8-9A-B)$	$B-A-(98-7-(6-54))^3*-21$
72BB	12527	$12+3-(-456-78*(9A+B))$	$B+A+9-(8-7-6)^5*4-3^2(-2-1)$
7300	12528	$1*-23*(-4+567-89A+B)$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6)^5*4-3+2-1$
7301	12529	$123+4-(5-6)-(-789-A)*B$	$-B-(A+9-(-8+7654))-321$
7302	12530	$1*2+3*(4^5 \wedge 6 / (7+8)+9)-(-A-B)$	$-B+A9*(8+76)-54-32+1$
7303	12531	$1-(2+3)-4*(-5^6+7-8-9)+A-B$	$B-A9*(-87+6)+(-5+4-3)*-2-1$
7304	12532	$-123-4-(-5+6+7-89)*AB$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6)^5*4+3-2+1$
7305	12533	$-1-2*-3456-7*(-89-A-B)$	$B+A9*(8+76)-5*4*-3*-2*1$
7306	12534	$12-3-(45+(-67-8-9)*AB)$	$B+A+987-(-6543+21)$
7307	12535	$-12+3*-456*-7-8*9A+B$	$-B+A+987+6543-2*1$
7308	12536	$1+23+45*(6-7)*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A+987+6543-2+1$
7309	12537	$-1+2+3-4*-5*6*7-8-9A+B$	$B-A+987-(-6543-2*-1)$
730A	12538	$(-1+2)*3-4*(-5^6+7-8-9)+A-B$	$B-(A-987-6543+2-1)$
730B	12539	$1^2+3-4*(-5^6+7-8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A*(-987-6543)-2*-1$
7310	12540	$-1*2*-3*(-45-6*7-(-89-A))*-B$	$-B*-A*(98+76-54-(3+21))$
7311	12541	$1234+5-(67-8+9)*-AB$	$-BA+98+7654-321$
7312	12542	$-1+234+567+8*9AB$	$B-A-(-987-6543-2)+1$
7313	12543	$-1*(-234-5-6)*(-78-(-9A-B))$	$-B-A-9*(8^7+6-(5+4)^3*2)^1$
7314	12544	$1-23+4-(5+6+78)*(9-AB)$	$-B-A-9*(8^7+6-(5+4)^3*2)+1$
7315	12545	$-1+2345-678*-9-A+B$	$-B-A-9-(-8-7654)-321$
7316	12546	$-1*-2*(-3+4567-8-9AB)$	$-B+A*(9+876+5)+(4-3)*-2-1$
7317	12547	$-12-3*45*-67-8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8+7654-321$
7318	12548	$1-23*(4-56)+(-78+9)*-AB$	$B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5-4/3^2-2)-1$
7319	12549	$12-3*-45*67+89-AB$	$-B+A-(9+8-7654+321)$
731A	12550	$(-1-2*3^4)*(-5*6-7*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(9-(8-7-6)^5)^4-(3*2+1)$
731B	12551	$-12-3*-45*67-(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$B*(A9+876+5*-43+21)$
7320	12552	$1-2*(3-4^5*6+(-7-8)^9)+A-B$	$B+A+(9-(8-7-6)^5)^4-3*2+1$
7321	12553	$1234+5-(-6+78)*(9-AB)$	$B+A+9-((-8-7*-6*5)*(-4^3+2)+1)$
7322	12554	$((1+2)^3+3+4)*(-5+6*7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8-7*6*5)*(-4^3+2)^1$
7323	12555	$1+((-2*-3)^4-(5+(-6-7)*8))^9+A-B$	$B-A9*(-87+6)-(-5-43+21)$
7324	12556	$-1+(-2+(-3+4^5/6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+987+6543-2-1$
7325	12557	$(-1-2+3^4)*(-5*(-6^7+8)-9)+A-B$	$B+A+987-(-6543+2)*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7326	12558	$-12^*(-3+4-(567-8+9A-B))$	$B+A+987+6543-2+1$
7327	12559	$-12-34^*-56+7^*(-8+9AB)$	$B+A+987-6543^*(-2+1)$
7328	12560	$-1^*(-23-45)^*(-67+89+AB)$	$B+A-(-987-6543-2+1)$
7329	12561	$1^{\wedge}2+3-4^*(-5^{\wedge}(6+7-8) -9)+A+B$	$B+A+987+6543+2^*1$
732A	12562	$-1-234+5+6-78^*(-9-AB)$	$-B+A+987-(-6543-21)$
732B	12563	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5^*6-(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8+7654-321$
7330	12564	$-123-456+789A+B$	$B-A-(-987-6543-21)$
7331	12565	$1+23^*(4-56^*-7)-8-9-(-A+B)$	$-B-(-A+9)-(-8-7654)-321$
7332	12566	$1+2+3^*4^*-56-(-789A+B)$	$B+A+(9-8+7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
7333	12567	$1-(-2345-678^*9-A-B)$	$-B+A+9-8+7654-321$
7334	12568	$1+2+3^*-4^*(56-789)-A+B$	$-B^*-A-((9+(8-(7+6))^{\wedge}5)^*4-3^*-2^{\wedge}1)$
7335	12569	$((-1+2^*-3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*7/-8-9+A-B$	$B-A+9-8+7654-321$
7336	12570	$123+4^*-5-(6-(-789-A))^*-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5+4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
7337	12571	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(-5-6)^*7+8-9+A+B$	$B+A-9-8+7654-321$
7338	12572	$-12^*(3-4)^*(567-8+9A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-9+876)+5^*43+2^*-1$
7339	12573	$1-234-5^*(6-78)^*(9-(-A-B))$	$B^*(-A9+876-5-(4-32-1))$
733A	12574	$1-2-(-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8^*(7-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
733B	12575	$-1-2^*-3^*4^*(5+6-7)^*(8-9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9+(-8^*(7-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
7340	12576	$1^*-2^*3^*-4^*(-5-(6-7))^*(-8+9)^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7-6^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
7341	12577	$12+3^*4^*-56+789A-B$	$-B-A+(9-(8-(7-6))^{\wedge}5)/-4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1$
7342	12578	$1^*-2^*(3-4567-8+9AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7)^*-6+(5^*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
7343	12579	$1^*2+(-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7)^*(-6/5-4^{\wedge}3^*(2+1))$
7344	12580	$1+(-2-3)^*-4^*(-5+6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)^*(-6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1$
7345	12581	$-1-2^*-345+6789+AB$	$-BA9+8765-432-1$
7346	12582	$1^*-23^*(-4+56^*-7)^*((-8+9)^*-A+B)$	$-BA9+8765-432^*1$
7347	12583	$1+2^*345-(-6789-AB)$	$-B+A-(-9-8)+7654-321$
7348	12584	$-12-3-4+5+6^*(-7-8)^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A+987+6543+21$
7349	12585	$-1+23^*(45+6)^*7+8+9AB$	$B-A+9+8-(-7654+321)$
734A	12586	$12^*(-345-6+78-9A^*-B)$	$B+A-9^*(8^*7+6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^*2)+1$
734B	12587	$1-23^*(456-789)-AB$	$B+A-9-(-8-7654)-321$
7350	12588	$-1+23-(-45^*-6+78^*(-9-AB))$	$-B-A9^*(-87+6)-(-54+3)+21$
7351	12589	$-1-2+3-456-(-78-9)^*AB$	$B+A+9-8+7654-321$
7352	12590	$1+23+45^*-6+78^*(9+AB)$	$-B^*-A+(-9^*8+7)^{\wedge}(6-5)^*-4^{\wedge}3^*(2+1)$
7353	12591	$1+2^*(3+4567-(-8+9AB))$	$B+A^*(-9-(-876-54)-32-1)$
7354	12592	$-1-(-2345-6^*(7-(-8-9AB)))$	$-B-A+(-9-8)^*-7^*(-6-(5-4^{\wedge}3))^*2-1$
7355	12593	$-1+2+3-456+(-78-9)^*-AB$	$BA-98-(-7654+321)$
7356	12594	$1-(-2-(-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B+A^*987-(654+321)$
7357	12595	$1+2+3-456-(78+9)^*-AB$	$-B-A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
7358	12596	$1+2^*-34^*-56+7^*(-89+A)^*-B$	$BA-9876+54^*321$
7359	12597	$((-1+2)^*-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A+B$	$B+A+(9+8+7)^*(-6+(-5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
735A	12598	$-12+345-6+(-789+A)^*-B$	$-BA9+87-6^*-54^*(32-1)$
735B	12599	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3+4+5^*6)^*7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$BA9-(-8-7^*(6+543)^*2^*1)$
7360	12600	$12-3-45-(6+78)^*(-9A-B)$	$BA+9^*876+5-43^*-21$
7361	12601	$-1-2+34^*-56-(7-89AB)$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2^*1)$
7362	12602	$-12-345-(-67+89A)^*-B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+6-((-5-4)^{\wedge}3+2))+1$
7363	12603	$-1-(2-(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6)/(7-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8^*(-7-6)-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
7364	12604	$1+2345-(-67+8)^*(-9+AB)$	$-B-A9^*-87-6^*(-5-43)^*2^*1$
7365	12605	$-1+2-34^*56-(7-89AB)$	$B+A+9-(-8-7654+321)$
7366	12606	$-1^*(-23+4-(-56-789)-A)^*-B$	$-B^*(A-9)^*(8+765+43+2)^*-1$
7367	12607	$-1-2-345^*(-6+7)^*(89-AB)$	$B-A9^*-87-65-432^*1$
7368	12608	$1^{\wedge}2+3^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)+9)+A-B$	$-B^*-A-9-(8-7-6)^{\wedge}5^*4+3^*2+1$
7369	12609	$-123-4^*-5^*67^*8+9+AB$	$BA9+8^*(-76+543)^*-2^*-1$
736A	12610	$1+2+3^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
736B	12611	$(((1+2)^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5)^*(6+7+8-9)+A-B$	$B+A-(9-8^*7/((-6+5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
7370	12612	$1-(-2+(-3+4^{\wedge}5)/6+7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7^*(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
7371	12613	$-1-2^*-3456+7-8^*-9A+B$	$B+A-9-(-8^*7^*((-6+5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
7372	12614	$(-1/-2^*-3^*-4^{\wedge}5+6^*7)^*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9/-8+7)^*6^{\wedge}5/(4+3-2)-1$
7373	12615	$-1+2-3-4^*-56-(-789-A)^*B$	$-B-A+(-9/-8+7)^*6^{\wedge}5/(4+3-2^{\wedge}1)$
7374	12616	$-1-((2-3+4)^{\wedge}5^*-6+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A^*987-(654+321)$
7375	12617	$1-2-34^*56+7+89AB$	$B^*(A-9+87-65+4)^*(32-1)$
7376	12618	$12+34^*-56-7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7^*(-6-(5-4^{\wedge}3)))^*2+1$
7377	12619	$-1-(-2345-67^*(-8+9A)+B)$	$-BA-98^*(-76+5^*4)+(-3+2)^*-1$
7378	12620	$-1-23-4^*-5^*-67^*-8+9+A-B$	$-B+A9^*(8+76)+5+4+3^*-21$
7379	12621	$1+2+34^*-56+7+89AB$	$BA-987-6^*-543^*(2+1)$
737A	12622	$123+45^*6+(-789A)^*-B$	$B+A-9^*8^*7^*6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2^*1)$
737B	12623	$-1-2+(34-56-78)^*(-9A+B)$	$B+A-9^*8^*7^*6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)+1$
7380	12624	$1-2^*-3+4^*56+(-789-A)^*-B$	$B+A-9^*((-8+(7^*-6+5)^*4)/3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
7381	12625	$1-23-4^*5^*67^*-8+(-9A)^*B$	$-B^*-A+9-(8-7-6)^{\wedge}5^*4+3^*2^{\wedge}1$
7382	12626	$-1^*-2^*(3-45+6-7-8)^*(-9A+B)$	$-B-A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
7383	12627	$-1-234-567-89^*-AB$	$-B-A^*-987-65-43^*21$
7384	12628	$1^*-2^*(-3^*(-4+5)-67)^*(-8-9A)^*-B$	$B^*(A-(-9-87)-(65+4))^*(3+21)$
7385	12629	$1-234-(567-89^*AB)$	$-B^*-A+9+(-8+7+6)^{\wedge}5^*4+3^*2+1$
7386	12630	$-1+2-3+4^*5^*-67^*-8-9-A+B$	$-B-A+98^*(-7-6^*5^*-4)-321$
7387	12631	$(-1-2^*(-3-(-4^{\wedge}5+6))^*7)^*-8/9+A-B$	$-B+A-9^*-87+65^*-4^*-32+1$
7388	12632	$12+34^*-56-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-A+((-9+8^*7)^*-6^*-5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1$
7389	12633	$1-2^*3+45^*6-(7+89)^*-A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)-2^{\wedge}1$
738A	12634	$-1/((-2-3)/4)^*5^{\wedge}6-(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*(-6-(5-4^{\wedge}3))^*2-1$
738B	12635	$1-2^*-3-4^*-567-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(7-6^*5^{\wedge}4/(3+2)+1)$
7390	12636	$-1+2-(-34+5-6^*(-7-8)^*(-9-AB))$	$B+A^*(98+765)+432+1$
7391	12637	$-1^*(((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*-7+8)/9+A-B$	$BA-9^*8-(-7654+321)$
7392	12638	$123+4^*-5^*-6^*78+9AB$	$-BA^*(-98-7-6+5-4+32+1)$
7393	12639	$-123-4-56+78^*(9+AB)$	$-B^*(A-9-876+54+3+21)$
7394	12640	$-12+3-4^*-5^*67^*8^*(-9A)+B$	$B-A+9^*8+7654-321$
7395	12641	$-1+2345-67^*(8-9A)+B$	$B-A^*9^*-87+6^*5^*4^*(3+21)$
7396	12642	$1234+5678-9^*A^*B$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^*((6^*5+4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
7397	12643	$-1-2^*3+(45-6+789-A)^*B$	$-B-A-9^*(8-(7+(-6-5)^*-4^{\wedge}3^*2))+1$
7398	12644	$-12-(-3456-7^*-8^*(9-AB))$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^*(-6^*5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7399	12645	$-1+2+3+4-5+(-6-78)^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^*(-6^*-5+4+321)$
739A	12646	$12+3+45-(67+8+9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^*(-6^*5+4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
739B	12647	$-1+234+(5+6+78+9)^*-A^*-B$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+(-6-5)^*(-4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
73A0	12648	$1^*-2^*(-34-5-6)^*(-7-(8-9)^*AB)$	$B+A-9^*((-8-7^*-6+5)^*-4^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
73A1	12649	$(-1+2-3+4^5/6+7)^*8^9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+(-9-8+7)*((-6-(5^4+3))^2+1)$
73A2	12650	$1+234-5+6+(7+89)^*A^*B$	$-B^*(-A98+7-(-6+54-321))$
73A3	12651	$-1-(-2^*3-4^*(5^*(6+7-8)+9))+A^*B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(7-6^*5^4/(3+2))-1$
73A4	12652	$1+2^*3456+(78+9)^*A-B$	$-B+A98-7+6543-21$
73A5	12653	$(-1-2^*(-3-(-4^5+6))^*7)^*-8/9+A+B$	$-BA+987+65^*4^*(32-1)$
73A6	12654	$123^*(-45-(-6-7+8-(-9+AB)))$	$B-A9^*-87-6^*5-432^*1$
73A7	12655	$-12-3+4^*56^*(-78+9+AB)$	$BA+987-(-6543+21)$
73A8	12656	$1+2345+678^*9+A^*B$	$BA98+7^*-65-4321$
73A9	12657	$1+2^*3+(45-6+789-A)^*B$	$-B-A9^*(-8-76)-(-54-32)^*-1$
73AA	12658	$1+2^*3^*-4^*5^*6+789A+B$	$BA-9^*8^*-7-65^*4^*(-32-1)$
73AB	12659	$-1^*((-2^*-3)^4-5^*6)^*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-(8-7))^*(-6-(5^4+3))^*2^{\wedge}1$
73B0	12660	$-1-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*(5-6^*(7-8^*9))+A+B$	$-B-A+9+8^*(-7-6-5)^*-4^*(-3+21)$
73B1	12661	$1+2+3456-7^*8^*(9-AB)$	$B+A+((-9-8^*7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}3/-2^*1$
73B2	12662	$(-1+2^{\wedge}-3+4^*5+6)^*-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+98+7654-321$
73B3	12663	$-1-2^*-3456-78^*(-9+A)^*-B$	$-B^*-A+9+(-8^*(7-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
73B4	12664	$((1^{\wedge}2+3)^4-5^*6)^*7^*8+9A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*(-6^*(-5-4)^*(3+2))-1$
73B5	12665	$12-34^*-5^*(-6-7)+89AB$	$-B^*-A-A9^*(-8-7-6^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
73B6	12666	$1-2^*3^*-45-6-(789A)^*-B$	$-B+A98+7+6543-21$
73B7	12667	$1+((-2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)^*-6+7)^*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$-B+A^*(9-8)^*765+4^*321$
73B8	12668	$12+3+4^*5^*6^*7^*-8+(-9+A)^*B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
73B9	12669	$1+2+3+4-5-(-6-78)^*(9A+B)$	$-B+A9^*(87-6)-54^*-3-21$
73BA	12670	$-12^*(-3-(4+567-8)-(9A-B))$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
73BB	12671	$1+23-4+5+(-6-78)^*(-9A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(-8-7)^*(-6^*-5+4^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
7400	12672	$-1^*(2-3)^*-4^*56^*(78-9-AB)$	$B^*(A-9-(-8-7))^*(6+54+3-(2-1))$
7401	12673	$1234-567+8^*9AB$	$-B-(A-98^*7+(-6-5^*4)^*321)$
7402	12674	$-1-2^*-3456-(-78+9-A)^*B$	$-B+A98-7+6543-2-1$
7403	12675	$-1+2345+678^*9+AB$	$-B+A98-7-(-6543+2^*1)$
7404	12676	$-1^*(-2345-678^*9-AB)$	$-B+A98-7+6543-2+1$
7405	12677	$1+2345+678^*9+AB$	$-B+A9-8+7654-321$
7406	12678	$1+234+567+89^*-A^*-B$	$BA+987+6543+2^*-1$
7407	12679	$(-1-2/-3+(-4^{\wedge}5/-6+7)^*8)^*9-A^*B$	$-B-(-A98+7-6543-2^*1)$
7408	12680	$-1+234^*56+7^*(-89A-B)$	$-B-(-A98+7)-(-6543-2-1)$
7409	12681	$123+456-78^*(-9A-B)$	$BA+987-(-6543-2+1)$
740A	12682	$1-234^*-56+7^*(-89A-B)$	$BA+987+6543+2^*1$
740B	12683	$(-1/-2^*-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA+987+6543+2+1$
7410	12684	$12^*3^*(45+6+7+89+AB)$	$B-A9^*-87-(-6+5)-(-432+1)$
7411	12685	$-1-23-(456-(789A-B))$	$-BA9+8^*-76^*5^*-4-3+2-1$
7412	12686	$1^*-23-456+789A-B$	$B-A9^*-87+6-(5+432)+1$
7413	12687	$1-23-456-(-789A+B)$	$-BA9-8^*-76^*5^*4-(3-(2+1))$
7414	12688	$-1-2^*3^*((-4-(5-6))^{\wedge}7+8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A98+7+6543-(2+1)$
7415	12689	$123+4^*-5^*-6^*7^*8-(-9+AB)$	$-B-A^*(-987-(-65-43-2+1))$
7416	12690	$-1^*-23^*(4-(5+678-9AB))$	$-B+A98+7+6543-(2-1)$
7417	12691	$1+23^*(4-5-678+9AB)$	$-BA-98+7654-3^*21$
7418	12692	$-12-3^*-4^*(-5-6)+(-7+89)^*AB$	$-B+A98+7+6543+2-1$
7419	12693	$(-1-2/3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A+B$	$-B+A98+7-(-6543-2^*1)$
741A	12694	$-1^*(23+45+678+9A)^*-B$	$-B+A98-(-7-(6543+2))-1$
741B	12695	$-1-2-3^*-45^*6^*7+8+9A+B$	$-BA9+8-76^*5^*(-4-3-21)$
7420	12696	$-12-3-(456-789A+B)$	$B+A98-(7-6543+2+1)$
7421	12697	$1+23^*(456+789)-(A+B)$	$B+A98-7-(-6543+2)^*1$
7422	12698	$12^*(-34+567-(-8-9)+AB)$	$B+A98-7+6543-2+1$
7423	12699	$-1-2+3^*-4^*-5-(6+78)^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A9-8+7654-321$
7424	12700	$-1^*-2^*(-3+45)^*(6+7-(8+9)+AB)$	$B-(-A98+7-6543)+2-1$
7425	12701	$-1+234-(5+6)^*-789+AB$	$B+A98-7+6543+2^*1$
7426	12702	$-12+3-456+789A-B$	$B+A98-7+6543+2+1$
7427	12703	$1+2-34+(-5+6-78)^*(-9-AB)$	$BA98-7+65^*-43^*-2^*-1$
7428	12704	$1-23^*(-45-6)-(78+9)^*-A^*B$	$B-(-A-98-7654+321)$
7429	12705	$1+2-3^*-45^*6^*7+8^*(9A-B)$	$BA+987-(-6543-21)$
742A	12706	$12+3^*45^*6^*7+(-8+9)^*AB$	$B+A9+8^*7^*(6-54-3)^*-2^*1$
742B	12707	$-1-23-456+789A+B$	$-B-A-9^*(-8-7^*-6^*5)^*(-4-3)+2/1$
7430	12708	$-1^*(2+3+456-789A+B)$	$BA-9+8+7654-321$
7431	12709	$1-23-456+789A+B$	$-B-A+((9^*-8^*-7+6)^*-5+4)^*(-3^*2+1)$
7432	12710	$(-1-2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA+9-8+7654-321$
7433	12711	$-1-(-2+3)-(-456-789A+B)$	$B+A98+7+6543-2^*1$
7434	12712	$12^*(-34+56-7^*(-89-A-B))$	$B+A98+7+6543-2+1$
7435	12713	$-1234+567-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7)^*(-6^*-5+4^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
7436	12714	$-1^*(2-(3-456)-(789A-B))$	$B+A98+7-(-6543-2+1)$
7437	12715	$1-2+3-(456-789A+B)$	$B+A9+8-(-7654+321)$
7438	12716	$1234+56+7^*-8^*-9^*(A+B)$	$-B+A98+7+6543+21$
7439	12717	$-1+2+3-456+789A-B$	$BA98+7+65^*-43^*2^*1$
743A	12718	$-12-3-(456-789A-B)$	$-B+A+9^*876+543^*2-1$
743B	12719	$1+2+3-(456-789A-B)$	$-B+A+9^*876-543^*-2^*1$
7440	12720	$1-2^*-3-456+789A-B$	$BA+9^*876-(5+43)^*-21$
7441	12721	$-1+234^*(-5+67)+89^*-A^*B$	$B+A^*(987-65+43^*(-2+1))$
7442	12722	$-1^*(-2+345^*(67-89)-A^*B)$	$B+A-9+(8-7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$
7443	12723	$-1234+56^*-7+89AB$	$B+A-9+(8-7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2/1)$
7444	12724	$-12+3-456+789A+B$	$B+A98-(7-6543-21)$
7445	12725	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^*(7^*8+9))+A-B$	$B+A-(-9^*-8+7/-6^*5)^*-4^{\wedge}3^*(2+1)$
7446	12726	$1^*2^*(-34+567^*8+(9A-B)^*-B)$	$BA+9+8+7654-321$
7447	12727	$1-234-(56+7^*8)^*(-9A+B)$	$-BA-98-(-7654-(-32-1))$
7448	12728	$(-1+2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA-9^*-876+54^*(-3+21)$
7449	12729	$-1-(2+3)-(-456-789A-B)$	$-BA-98+7654-32+1$
744A	12730	$12+3-456-(-789A+B)$	$-BA+98^*76+54^*32^*1$
744B	12731	$1-2-(3+456-789A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8+7^*6)^*-5^*(-4^{\wedge}3+2)^*1$
7450	12732	$-1-23^*-4^*(5-6-(7-8-9A))-B$	$B-A^*-98^*7-6^*-543-21$
7451	12733	$-1+2-3-456+789A+B$	$-B-A+9-8^*(7-(-6^*-5^*4/-3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
7452	12734	$-1-23-(-4^*-5^*6^*7^*-8+9-AB)$	$-BA-98+7^*-654^*(-3-(-2+1))$
7453	12735	$-1-2-(-3+456-789A-B)$	$-BA+98765-4-321$
7454	12736	$-1^*(2-3+456-789A-B)$	$-B^*-A+9-8^*(7+(-6-5)^*(-4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
7455	12737	$1-2+3-456+789A+B$	$BA9+8^*(-7+654+321)$
7456	12738	$-1+2^*3456-78-9^*-AB$	$B+A98-(-7-6543)+21$
7457	12739	$-1-(-23+456)+789A-B$	$-B+A9^*87+65+432^*-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7458	12740	$-1 * (-23+456-789A+B)$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$
7459	12741	$1+23-456+789A-B$	$B+A * (-987-(-65-(43-2)))^* -1$
745A	12742	$-1+(-2-3+(-4+5*6)^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9+87^*(-65-43+2+1))$
745B	12743	$-1-2^*3456-(-789+A+B)$	$-BA9+8765+4-321$
7460	12744	$1^*-23^*(4-5+678-9AB)$	$-BA-98+7654+3-21$
7461	12745	$-1-(-2-3)-(4^*-5^*67^*8-9^*A)+B$	$B+A^*9+87^*(-6^*5^*-4+3)-21$
7462	12746	$12-(3-(-456+789A+B))$	$BA9-87-(-6543-(-2-1))$
7463	12747	$-1^*(23-456+7-(8-9))^*(A+B)$	$BA9-87+6543-2^*1$
7464	12748	$1-(-234-56+(789A+B))^*-B$	$BA9-87+6543-2+1$
7465	12749	$(-1-2^*(3-4^5))^*6-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+98-7^*(-6-54-3)^*21$
7466	12750	$-1+2-3^*-4567-8^*9A^*B$	$BA9-87+6543+2-1$
7467	12751	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)^*(6+7)^*8-9)+A+B$	$BA9-87+6543-2^*-1$
7468	12752	$12-(3+456-789A)+B$	$BA9-87+6543+2+1$
7469	12753	$1^*-2+((-3+4^5)/-6-7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-B^*-A+(-9+8^*7)^*(-6^*(-5-4)^*(3+2)-1)$
746A	12754	$12^*(-3-4-567-89)^*(A-B)$	$B-A-98^*-76-543^*(-2-1)$
746B	12755	$-1+2-(345^*6+78^*(-9A+B))$	$-B^*-A-9^*((-8+(7^*-6+5)^*4)/3^{\wedge}2-2-1)$
7470	12756	$-123+45-6-78^*(-9-AB)$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-(-6^*-5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$
7471	12757	$-1^*-2+((-3+4^5)/-6-7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-(-6^*-5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
7472	12758	$12-34-567^*(-8-(9+A-B))$	$B+A+(-9-(8+7^*-6^*5))^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
7473	12759	$-1-2^*3^*4+567^*(8-(-9-A+B))$	$-B+A^*(9+876+54-32^*1)$
7474	12760	$123-456+(78+9)^*AB$	$-BA-(98-7654)-3^*-2^*-1$
7475	12761	$-1-(-23+456-789A-B)$	$-B-A9^*-87-(-6+54+321)$
7476	12762	$-12-34^*5-(-67+8+9)^*-AB$	$B+A9^*87+65-432+1$
7477	12763	$1+23-456+789A+B$	$-BA-9^*(-876-54^*3)-2+1$
7478	12764	$12+3-4^*5^*67^*8-(-9A+B)$	$-BA-98-(-7654-(-3+2)+1)$
7479	12765	$-1+2^*3456+789-(A-B)$	$-BA-98+7654-3+2^*1$
747A	12766	$-1^*2^*(-345-6)^*(78+9^*-A+B)$	$-BA-(98-7654)-(-3-2)+1$
747B	12767	$1-2^*-3456-(-789+A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(8-(7+6^*5))^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7480	12768	$-123+45+6-78^*(-9-AB)$	$-BA-98-(-7654-3+2-1)$
7481	12769	$(-1^*2/(-3+4-5^*6)^*(-7^*8^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A-9+8^*(7^*6+5-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7482	12770	$(-1-2^*(-3-4^*-5)^*6^*7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA-98-(-7654-3)-(-2+1)$
7483	12771	$1-2-3+456+(-789+A)^*B$	$-B^*(A9-876+5+(-43+2)^*-1)$
7484	12772	$-1-2^*3-45-6+(7-89)^*-AB$	$-BA-98+7654+3^*2^*1$
7485	12773	$1-2^*345-(6+7)-89^*-AB$	$-BA-98+7654-3^*-2+1$
7486	12774	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3-4)^*(-5+(-6-7)^*8)^*9+A+B$	$BA9-87-(-6543-21)$
7487	12775	$(-1+(-2-3)^*-4^5/6)^*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$-BA-98-(-7654+3^*(-2-1))$
7488	12776	$1234-5+(-678-(9+A))^*-B$	$-BA9-87-6^*54^*-32^*1$
7489	12777	$1+2-34-56+78^*(9+AB)$	$-BA9-87+6^*54^*32+1$
748A	12778	$-1+2^*3456+7-8^*(-9-AB)$	$-B-A+(-9^*-8+7)^*-6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3/2)+1$
748B	12779	$-123+4+56-78^*(-9-AB)$	$-B-A+(-9/-8^*-7+6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$
7490	12780	$12-3-(4^*-5^*67^*8-(9A+B))$	$-BA^*(9-8+7+65+(-4+3)^*-21)$
7491	12781	$-12+34^*5-6-7^*89^*(-A-B)$	$BA+9^*8+7654-321$
7492	12782	$1+23^*45+6789-AB$	$-BA+9^*-8+7654-(3+21)$
7493	12783	$-12-3^*-45^*67+89+AB$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7-6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*-3^*(2-1)$
7494	12784	$1-2^{\wedge}3+(-4^5/-6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*87^*6-5+4321$
7495	12785	$123-45^*(-6-(78+9)-AB)$	$-B+A^*(-9+876)+5-(-4-321)$
7496	12786	$1-2^*(3-4^5^*6)-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A98^*-7+65-4^*-321$
7497	12787	$1+2^*3456-(-789-A)+B$	$-B-A-9+87^*-6^*5^*-4+321$
7498	12788	$12-(34+56-78^*(9+AB))$	$-BA-(98-7654+3-21)$
7499	12789	$-123+4-567+89^*AB$	$-B-A^*(987-65-4-32)^*-1$
749A	12790	$-1-23+4-56+78^*(9+AB)$	$-BA-9-8+7654+3^*-21$
749B	12791	$12+34^*5-6+7+89A^*B$	$B-A^*(-987-6)+5+43^*-21$
74A0	12792	$1-(23-(4-56)+78^*(-9-AB))$	$B+A-9^*(8-7^*-6^*(-5-4^*3)^*2+1)$
74A1	12793	$-12-3-(4+56-78^*(9+AB))$	$-BA-(9-8)-7^*65^*4^*(-3-2-1)$
74A2	12794	$(-1+2)^*3+(-4^5/-6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA-(98-7654-3-21)$
74A3	12795	$-1-23-4-5-6+(-7+89)^*AB$	$-BA+9-8-7^*65^*-4^*-3^*2^*-1$
74A4	12796	$1^*2^*(-3-4)^*(-567-(8+9A-B))$	$BA9+8^*-7+6543^*(2-1)$
74A5	12797	$-1^*-2^*(3+4^5^*6)-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$BA9+8^*-7+6543-(-2+1)$
74A6	12798	$1^*(-2+3)^*(-4-(56+78))^*(9^*-A+B)$	$B-A^*(9-876)^*(5-4)+321$
74A7	12799	$12-3+4+567^*(8+9-(A+B))$	$B+A+9+(8-7^*(-6+5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2/1$
74A8	12800	$-1^*(-2+3+4+5)^*(-6+7-89A-B)$	$B+A+9+((-8-7)^*6-5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
74A9	12801	$-1-23-4^*-5^*-67^*-8-9^*(-A-B)$	$-B-(A9+8-7654+3^*21)$
74AA	12802	$1-(-2+34)-5+6-(-7+89)^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(8-7^*-6^*(-5-4^*3)^*2)+1$
74AB	12803	$12345-6-78^*(9A+B)$	$-BA-(98-(7654+32-1))$
74B0	12804	$-12-3-45-6+78^*(9+AB)$	$-B-(A9-8)+7^*-65^*(4-(3+21))$
74B1	12805	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5)/-6+7)^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$-BA-98+7654+32+1$
74B2	12806	$-1+23+4^*5^*67^*8+9+AB$	$-BA-9+8-(-7654+3^*21)$
74B3	12807	$1234-567+89^*A^*B$	$B+A+9+8+(7-6^*5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
74B4	12808	$12-3^*45^*6-7-89^*-AB$	$-BA+9-8+7654+3^*-21$
74B5	12809	$(-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*-6/7)^*-8/9-(A-B)$	$-BA+98+(76-5)^*(-4^*-32-1)$
74B6	12810	$-12^*(3-4-567-8-9A+B)$	$-BA-9^*8+7654-3+2+1$
74B7	12811	$((-1-(-2/-3+4^5))/-6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*(7^*6+5-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
74B8	12812	$1+(-2+((-3-4^5)/-6+7)^*8)^*9-(A-B)$	$BA9-8-7+6543-21$
74B9	12813	$-1+2345-(6-7^*89A+B)$	$B+A-9+8^*(7^*6+5-4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
74BA	12814	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5-6^*(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*-8+7654+3+2-1$
74BB	12815	$1-(-2345+6)-7^*-89A-B$	$-BA+9^*-8-(-7654-3+2^*-1)$
7500	12816	$-12-3-45+6+78^*(9+AB)$	$-BA-9^*8+7654-3^*2^*-1$
7501	12817	$-1+2+3^*-4^*(56-789-A-B)$	$-B-A9+8-(-7654+3^*21)$
7502	12818	$1^*(2-3)^*(-4+56+78^*(-9-AB))$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7)^*-6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3/2)-1$
7503	12819	$1^{\wedge}2-(-3-(-4^5/-6+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*((8-7^*6+5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
7504	12820	$1^*2-(-3-(-4^5/-6+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA-9^*-876+5^*4^*-3^*-21$
7505	12821	$1+2+(-3-(4^5/-6-7)^*-8)^*-9+A-B$	$BA9+8^*-7-(-6543-21)$
7506	12822	$(-1-2^*(3-4^5^*6)^*7)^*8)/9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8^*(7+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^*2)^{\wedge}1$
7507	12823	$-12-(-3+4)-(-5+(6-7-8)^*9AB)$	$-BA9+8^*-7-6^*-54^*32^*1$
7508	12824	$1+2+3+4-56-78^*(-9-AB)$	$-BA+9+8+7654+3^*-21$
7509	12825	$-1-(-2345-6)-(-7^*-89A+B)$	$BA+98+7654-321$
750A	12826	$-1^*(2-3+4-56-789A)^*B$	$-BA-9-(8-7654)-(-32+1)$
750B	12827	$-1-2-(3^*-4^*(5+678)+9A^*-B)$	$B-A9^*-87-654+321$
7510	12828	$-12+3^*(-4-567)+89AB$	$BA9+8-7+6543-21$
7511	12829	$1+2+3-4-5-6-(-7+89)^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(7^*6+5-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
7512	12830	$-1-23^*-4^*-5-(-6-789A-B)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7^*6+5-4-3)^{\wedge}2/1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7513	12831	1234+5678+9*AB	B+A+9+8*(7*6+5-4-3)^2+1
7514	12832	12-3-45-6+78*(9+AB)	-B+A-98+7654+3*-21
7515	12833	1-2*-345-6+78*(9A+B)	B+A+9/8+7*(6+5)^4/(3^2-1)
7516	12834	-1-234*-56-7*(89A-B)	-B-A-9*-8*76+5*-43*-21
7517	12835	-1+2345-6+7*89A+B	BA9-8-(7-6543-2*-1)
7518	12836	-1*(-2345+6-7*89A-B)	BA9-(8+7-6543)-(2-1)
7519	12837	1*23-4-56+78*(9+AB)	-B-A9-8-(7654+32)-1
751A	12838	12*(-3+4-56+789-AB)	-B-A9+87*(65+43+2*-1)
751B	12839	1-2*-3*4-56+78*(9+AB)	B-A9+8+7654+3*-21
7520	12840	-1-2+345*6-7*(8-9AB)	BA9-(8+7-(6543+2+1))
7521	12841	1^2-(-3-(-4^5/-6+7)*8)*9+A+B	-BA-(98-7654)-3*-21
7522	12842	-1-234-(567+89A*-B)	BA9+8+7+6543-21
7523	12843	-1+2*-34*5*6-(7-89AB)	-BA-9-8+7654-(-3+21)
7524	12844	1-23*4*5+6+789A+B	-BA+9-(8-7654+32+1)
7525	12845	1234-(56-78*9A+B)	-BA+9-8+7654-32*1
7526	12846	1-2*(34-5)*6+7*-89*-AB	-BA-9-8+7654-32+1
7527	12847	(-1*-2+((-3-4^5)/-6+7)*8)*9-(A-B)	-BA-9*-8-(7654-32)-1
7528	12848	1+(-2*-3+(-4^5/-6+7)*8)*9-(A-B)	-B-A-(98-(7654-32))-1
7529	12849	1+23*(-456+789)+AB	BA9-8-(7-6543-2*-1)
752A	12850	1-2-34+5+6+78*(9+AB)	BA9+8-7+6543-2-1
752B	12851	-1-(2-34+56-78*(9+AB))	-B-A-98*-76+54*-32*-1
7530	12852	1*23*(45-6*-78-9A-B)	BA9+8-7+6543-2+1
7531	12853	12-3*4*5*(6-78-9A)+B	-BA-9-(8-7654+3+21)
7532	12854	-123-45*6*7+89AB	B-(-A+98-7654-3*-21)
7533	12855	(-1+2*(-3-(-4^5+6))*7)*-8/9+A-B	-BA+9-(8-7654)-3-21
7534	12856	1-23+4*(5+6)-(-7+89)*-AB	BA9+8-7+6543+2+1
7535	12857	-1-(2+3-4)-(56+789-A)*-B	B-A9+(87-(6-54))*3*21
7536	12858	12+345+6*(789A+)*-B	-B-(A+98)+765*-4*-3-21
7537	12859	1-2*34*5*6+7+89AB	-B-(A+98)+7654-(3+21)
7538	12860	1*23-45+6-78*(-9-AB)	B-A9-87*(-65-43+2)*1
7539	12861	-1-(2+345+6)-(-789A+B)	-BA+9+8+7654-32*1
753A	12862	-12-345+6+789A-B	BA9-8-7+6543+21
753B	12863	-1+2*-345+6+789*AB	-BA9-(8+7+6*54*-32+1)
7540	12864	-12+3-4+5-6-78*(-9-AB)	BA9+8+7+6543-2-1
7541	12865	-1+2-(345+6-789A)-B	-B-(A+98-7654-3)-21
7542	12866	-1*-2*(3-(-456+789A)-B)	BA9-(8-7-6543)-(2-1)
7543	12867	-1+2-(3*(-4+56+7)-89AB)	-BA-9-(8-7654)-(-3-(-2+1))
7544	12868	1*-23+4+5+6-78*(-9-AB)	-B+A-98+7654-32-1
7545	12869	1+((2+3)^4/-5*-6+7)*(8+9)+A-B	BA9-(8-7-6543+2*-1)
7546	12870	1*(23-4-56-7*-8)*9*A*B	BA9+8-(-7-(6543+2+1))
7547	12871	-12-3*-45+6*(78+9)*(A+B)	-BA+9+8+7654-3-21
7548	12872	-12-345-6+789A+B	B-A-98+7654-32+1
7549	12873	1234-56-(78-9)*-AB	B+A+9*(8*7-(6-5*4)^3/2)^1
754A	12874	-1*(2+345-(6+789A-B))	-B-(A9+8)-(-7654+3-2)-1
754B	12875	1-2-345+6+789A-B	-BA-9+8-(7654-3*2*-1)
7550	12876	-12+34-5*6-78*(-9-AB)	B-(A9+8-7654-3)-21
7551	12877	-1+2-(345-6)+789A-B	-BA-9-8+7654-3-(2+1)
7552	12878	12-345-6+789A-B	-BA9-(8-7-6*54*-32*1)
7553	12879	1+2-345-(6-789A+B)	-B+A-98+7654-3-21
7554	12880	-1*2*(3+4)*(-567+8-9A-B)	-BA9+8-7+6*54*-32*-1
7555	12881	-1*(234+5+6+78-9A)*-B	-BA-9+8+7654-3+2+1
7556	12882	(-1+2+(3/-4+5)*6*-7*8)*9+A+B	-B-A9-(8-7654-3*2*1)
7557	12883	-1-2-345-6+789A+B	-BA-9-8+7654-(3-2-1)
7558	12884	-12-345+6+789A+B	-BA-(9+8)-(-7654-3+2*1)
7559	12885	1-2-345-6+789A+B	-BA+9-8+7654-(-3+2-1)
755A	12886	1*(-2+3)*(4-5)*(-6-78*(9+AB))	-B-A9+8+7654-3*-2*-1
755B	12887	-1-(2+345+6-789A-B)	-B-A-(98-7654)+3-2-1
7560	12888	-123+45*-6+789A+B	-B-A9-(8-7654+3)-(2-1)
7561	12889	1+2-(345+6-789A-B)	-B-(A9-8)-765*4*-3-(-2+1)
7562	12890	12-345+6+789A-B	B-(-A+98)-(-7654+32+1)
7563	12891	1*2-(-3+(-4*-5+6)*7)*-8*9-(A-B)	B-A9-(8-7654-3*-2+1)
7564	12892	-12-34-(-56-78*(9+AB))	BA9+8+7+6543+21
7565	12893	(-1-2*3*-4^5/6+7*8)*9+A*B	-BA-9-8+7654+3+21
7566	12894	-12*(345+6+7+8-9AB)	-BA-(9-8)+7654-(3-2*-1)
7567	12895	1+2*3456-(-7*-8+9A*-B)	-BA-(9-8)-(-7654+3-(-2+1))
7568	12896	-1*(2+345-(6+789A+B))	-B-A9+8+7654-(-3-2)-1
7569	12897	1-2-345+6+789A+B	-BA+9-(8-(7654-3)-2+1)
756A	12898	-12+3*-4*(5+6+78-9*AB)	B-(A9+8)+7654-(3-(2+1))
756B	12899	-1+2-345+6+789A+B	B-A9-8-(-7654-3-2*-1)
7570	12900	-1*(-2+345-(6+789A)-B)	B+A-98-765*-4*3-21
7571	12901	1+2-345+6-(-789A-B)	-BA+9+8+7654+3-2+1
7572	12902	-12-34-(567-89*AB)	-BA-(9+8-(7654+32-1))
7573	12903	1-(-2345+6+7*(-89A-B))	-BA-9+8+7654-(3-21)
7574	12904	-12+3-(-4*-5*6*7-89*AB)	-BA-(9+8-7654-(32+1))
7575	12905	1+2*3456-(7-89A+B)	-BA-(9+8)-(-7654-(-3+21))
7576	12906	123-(456-789A-B)	B-(-A+98-7654)-(-3-2)*1
7577	12907	(1+2)^3*(4-5*6-7*-8*9)-(A-B)	-BA-(9-8)-(7654-3*(-2-1))
7578	12908	-12*(3+4-567-8+9-AB)	-BA+9+8+7654-3*(-2-1)
7579	12909	(-1+2*3*4-5*6*7)*-8*9+A+B	B-A-(98-7654)-(-3-2-1)
757A	12910	-123+4*-5-(67-89A)*B	-B-A*9-8+7654-3-2*1
757B	12911	-1+23*45+6789*(-A+B)	B-A9*-87+6+54-321
7580	12912	12-345+6+789A+B	B-(A9-8-7654)-3-(-2+1)
7581	12913	-1-(2+34)-(567-89*AB)	-B-A9-8+7654+32-1
7582	12914	-1*(2-(3+4+56)-(789-A))*B	-B-A9-(8-7654+3-21)
7583	12915	12+34*-5-(67-89A)*B	-BA-9*-8+7654-32-1
7584	12916	-12+3-(-45+6-78*(9+AB))	B+A*-9+8-(-7654+32)+1
7585	12917	1-2+3+4*-5*-6*-7-89*-AB	-B*-A+9*(8+7+(-6-5)*-4^3*2)^1
7586	12918	1234-5-6+(-78-9)*-AB	B-A9+8+7654+3-(-2+1)
7587	12919	1+2-34-567-89*-AB	-BA-9+8+7654+32*1
7588	12920	12-34+56-78*(-9-AB)	B-A9-(8-7654)-3+21
7589	12921	-1+23+4+5+6+78*(9+AB)	-BA+9+8+7654-3+21

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
758A	12922	1234+5-6-(-78*9A-B)	B+A-98+7654-3*2-1
758B	12923	(-1+2-(3/-4+5)*-6*7)*8*9+A-B	-BA-(-98-7654-3*-21)
7590	12924	1+234-5-6*(-7-8)*(9+AB)	-B-A-98+7654+32-1
7591	12925	-1-2*-3456-(7-89A)+B	-B-A-98+7654-32*-1
7592	12926	1-23-(4+567-89*AB)	B-A9-(8-(7654-(-3-21)))
7593	12927	-1+2*3*45*(-6*-7+8-9)-A*B	-BA-(-9-8-7654)-(-3-21)
7594	12928	1*2*(34+(56+7)*8*(9-A))*-B	B+A-98+7654-3+2*1
7595	12929	(-1-2*(3-4*5*6))*-7*-8-9-A*B	-B-(A9-8)-(-7654-32)-1
7596	12930	12-(34+567)+89*AB	BA9+87+6543-21
7597	12931	1+23+(-4-(56+789-A))*-B	-B-A9-(-8-7654)-(-32-1)
7598	12932	-1-23+4-567+89*AB	-B-A-(-9-8)+7*65*(-4+3+21)
7599	12933	12+34+5-(6-78*(9+AB))	BA9+8*7-(-6543-21)
759A	12934	1-(23-4)-(567+89*-AB)	B+A-98+7654+3-2*-1
759B	12935	-123-456-7+89*AB	-B+A-98-(-7654-3-21)
75A0	12936	12*3*-4*(-5+6)*(7-89+A+B)	-BA+9+8+7654+32-1
75A1	12937	(-1-((-2*-3+4^5)/6+7))*-8*9-(A-B)	-BA+9+8+7654+32*1
75A2	12938	-1*(-2^3-3*4^5*6+7)*8+9-(A-B)	-BA+9-(-8-7654-32)+1
75A3	12939	1-2+(3+4)^5-6^7/8/9+A+B	-B+A*(-9-876+5-43+2)*-1
75A4	12940	123+4*-5*6*7*-8-(-9-A-B)	-B-A*(9*8-7654+3*(-2-1))
75A5	12941	-12+3-4-567+89*AB	-B-A9+8765+4*-321
75A6	12942	-123+4*-56-(-789A-B)	B-A9+8+7654+3+21
75A7	12943	1-2-3*4-567-89*-AB	B+A-9+(-8-7*-6*5)/4^4-3+2+1
75A8	12944	1*2*3*-45+(-67+89A)*B	-B+A-98-(-7654-32+1)
75A9	12945	12-(-34-5)-(-6+78*(-9-AB))	-B+A-98+(-7654-32)*-1
75AA	12946	-1-2*(-3456-7)-(-89A-B)	-B-(-A+98-7654)-(-32-1)
75AB	12947	1*(-23-45+6-789+A)*-B	B-(-A-9*-8*7*6+5-4321)
75B0	12948	1+2345-67*(8+9-AB)	B-(-A-(-98+7654)-(-32+1))
75B1	12949	-123-456+7-89*-AB	-B-A*(9*-876-54*(3+21))
75B2	12950	1234+5678+9A*B	B+A-9*(8-7*(-6+5^4)/3)+2*1
75B3	12951	1-2*3456*(7-8)-9A*-B	B-A9+8+7654+32-1
75B4	12952	-1-2-(-3+4+567+89*-AB)	BA9+87+6543-(2+1)
75B5	12953	1234+5*6-78*-9A+B	B-A9+8+7654+32+1
75B6	12954	-12+3*4-567-89*-AB	BA9+87+6543-2+1
75B7	12955	1+2*-3+4-(567+89*-AB)	-BA-9*-8+(-7654-3+2)*-1
75B8	12956	1-2-(3-4)-(567-89*AB)	BA9+87+6543+2-1
75B9	12957	-1-2+3*4*(-5+678+9A+B)	B+A-98+7654+3+21
75BA	12958	-1*2*(-3-456-7*-8*(-9+A))*B	BA9+87+6543+2+1
75BB	12959	1-2*(345-678-9A)*B	-BA-(-98-7654)-32-1
7600	12960	-1-234-56+789A-B	-BA+98+7654-32*1
7601	12961	1*-234-56-(-789A+B)	-BA+98+7654-32+1
7602	12962	1-234-56-(-789A+B)	-BA+9*-8*(-76-54-3-21)
7603	12963	12-34*56-7*(8+9)*-AB	B-A9+8765+4*-321
7604	12964	12*(3-45-6+789-AB)	-B+A9*87-65*4-3-(2-1)
7605	12965	-1+23+45+6-78*(-9-AB)	-B+A-(-9-8)+7654+3*-21
7606	12966	1*2*3*(456+78+9AB)	B+A-98+7654+32-1
7607	12967	1+23+45+6+78*(9+AB)	-B-(A-9+8)-(-7654+32-1)
7608	12968	(1+2+3)^4*(5+6+7-8)+9+A-B	-B-(-A+9+8-7654+32*1)
7609	12969	12+3-4-567+89*AB	-B+A-(9+8-(7654-32))+1
760A	12970	-1+2*-3*4*5-6+789A+B	-BA+98+7654-3-21
760B	12971	(1/-2+3+4^5/6+7)*8*9+A-B	B-(A+9+8-(7654-32+1))
7610	12972	1-2*3*4*5-(6-789A)+B	B+A-9-(-8-7)*6^5/(4+3+2/1)
7611	12973	-1-(-2^3+(4^5/-6-7)*8)*9+A*B	B-A9-8+7654-3*-21
7612	12974	-1+234+5-(6+78)*(-9A-B)	-B-A-9+8+7654-3-21
7613	12975	(-1+(-2+3^4+5*6)*7)*(8+9)+A+B	B+A9*87+6*(-5-43+2)+1
7614	12976	1*-2*(-3-(-4-56*(7-89)+A+B))	-BA+98+7654-(-3+21)
7615	12977	-12+3*45-6-(7-89)*AB	B+A-9*(8-(-7/6+(5+4)^3))*2-1
7616	12978	-1+23-4-567+89*AB	B+A-9-8+7654-3-21
7617	12979	12345+6+7*-8*(-9-A)*-B	B+A+(-9+8-7*-6*5)*(4^3-2*1)
7618	12980	1+23-4-(567+89*-AB)	-B*A*(9-8)*(-76-(-5-4+32-1))
7619	12981	(-1-((-2*3)^4-(5-6)))*(7-(8+9))-(A-B)	-B-A-(-9-(8+7654-32))-1
761A	12982	-12+34-567+89*AB	-B-A*(9+8-7654)-(-3+2-1)
761B	12983	123-(-4+5*6+(-7+89))*-AB	-B+A-(9-8-7654)-(32+1)
7620	12984	-12+3+456+(-789-A)*-B	-B+A-9-8+7654+3-21
7621	12985	-1234+5*-6*7+89AB	-B+A+9-8+7654-32-1
7622	12986	-1-23*(456+7*8-9*AB)	-B-A-9-8+7654-3+2+1
7623	12987	-1-(-2-34-(56+78*(9+AB)))	-B-(-A-9)-(8-7654+32-1)
7624	12988	-1-2*345-(6-7+89A)*-B	-B+A+9*-8+7654+32-1
7625	12989	-1-234*-5+6789-AB	B-(-A+9)-(8-7654+32+1)
7626	12990	-1*(2-3)*(4+5+6)*(7*89+AB)	-B-A-9-(-8+7654))-(-3-2+1)
7627	12991	-1+(-2-3)^4/(-5/(-6-7))*8-9-(A-B)	B*(A98-7*(-6+5+43))-21)
7628	12992	1*(2+3)^4/-5*(-6-7)*8-9-(A-B)	-BA+98+7654-3-2-1
7629	12993	-1-2-(-34+567-89*AB)	-B+A9-87*(-65-(43-2)+1)
762A	12994	(-1-2*-3*4)*-5*(6-7*(8+9))+A-B	-BA+98-(-7654-(-3-2))-1
762B	12995	12+3*4-(5+6)*(-7+8)*-9*AB	B-(-A+9*8-7654+3-21)
7630	12996	-1-234-5*6+789A-B	-B+A+9-(8-7654+3)-21
7631	12997	-1+2+34-567-89*-AB	-BA+98-765*-4*3-(-2-1)
7632	12998	-1+2*-3*-4-5-(-6-7-89)*A*B	B-A+9-(8-7654)-3-21
7633	12999	1+2+34-567-89*-AB	-B-A+(-9-8)*7654-3-2+1
7634	13000	(-1+(-2*-3)^4/-5)*(-6*7-8)-9+A-B	-B-A-9+8+7654-3+2-1
7635	13001	(-1+(-2*3)^4+5)*-6*(-7-8)/9-(A-B)	-B-(-A+9+8-7654+3+2*1)
7636	13002	1*(234+56)*(7-89+AB)	B-A-9+8-(-7654-3+21)
7637	13003	-12+3*4*-5*6-(-789A-B)	B-A+9+8+7654-32-1
7638	13004	-123+4-567+89A*B	-B-A+9-8+7654-3+2+1
7639	13005	1234+56-(-78-9)*-AB	B-A-(-9-8-7654+32-1)
763A	13006	12*(-34+5+678-(-9-A+B))	-B-A-9+8+7654+3+2-1
763B	13007	-1+(2+3)^4/-5*(-6-7)*8+9+A-B	B-(-A-9+8-7654-(-32-1))
7640	13008	-1*2*3*4*(5-6*7-8+9*-AB)	B-A-9-8+7654-(-3+2+1)
7641	13009	-1-2*-345+(6-78)*(-9-AB)	B+A+9-8+7654-(-32-1)
7642	13010	12+34-567-89*-AB	-B-(A-9)-8-(-7654-(3+2+1))
7643	13011	1-23-45*6+789A-B	BA-98+7654-32-1
7644	13012	((-1-2)^4(3+4)+5)*-6-(7+8*9)+A-B	BA-98+7654+32*-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7645	13013	$-123-(45-6-(-78-9))*-AB$	$BA-98+7654-32+1$
7646	13014	$-12+3-45*6*7+89AB$	$B-A+9+8+7654-3-21$
7647	13015	$-1-234-5-6+789A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4))*3-2*1$
7648	13016	$1*-234-5-6+789A-B$	$-B-A-(-9-8-7654+3-(-2+1))$
7649	13017	$1-234-(5-(-6+789A))-B$	$B-(-A-9+8-765*4*-3+21)$
764A	13018	$-1-(234+5*6-(789A+B))$	$-B+A-(-9-8-7654)-(-3+21)$
764B	13019	$1-2-(-34-5-67)*-89*(A-B)$	$-B+A+9-8+7654-3-2*1$
7650	13020	$1234+56*7-8*9AB$	$-BA+98+7654-3+21$
7651	13021	$-1+23*45+6789-A*-B$	$-B+A+9+8-(76-5)*(-4*32-1)$
7652	13022	$-1+2*3456+7*-8+9AB$	$BA-98+7654-3-21$
7653	13023	$-1/-2*(-3+(-4-5^{\wedge}6))*(-7-8))/9+A-B$	$B-A+9-8-(-765*4*-3-2+1)$
7654	13024	$1-(2-34)+5-(-6-7-89)*-A*-B$	$B*(-A9+876-5+43+21)$
7655	13025	$-1+2345-67*8-(9A-B)$	$B-A-9+8+7654+3-2*1$
7656	13026	$-123-4-5*6+(-78-9)*-AB$	$B-(-A+9+8-7654+3-2+1)$
7657	13027	$-1-(234+5)+6-(-789A+B)$	$B-A+9-8+7654+3-2*1$
7658	13028	$-1*(234+5-6-789A+B)$	$B-(-A+9)-(8-7654-3)-(-2+1)$
7659	13029	$1-(234+5-6)-(-789A+B)$	$B+A9*87-65*4-(-32-1)$
765A	13030	$-1+(-2^{\wedge}3+(-4+5*6)*7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-(9+8-7654-3)-(-2-1)$
765B	13031	$-12-3-45+(67-89A)*-B$	$-B+A9*87-(65+4)*3-2*1$
7660	13032	$1-23+4-(56+7*8)*(-9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-9+8-7654)+3+21$
7661	13033	$1-234+5*-67+89*AB$	$B+A-9-(8-(7654+3-2*-1))$
7662	13034	$123+4+(56+789-A)*B$	$-B+A-(-9-(8+7654))-3-2-1$
7663	13035	$-1*-2*(-3-4)*5(-6-7)*-8*9)-(A-B)$	$-BA-98-(-7654-32)-1$
7664	13036	$-12+3456+7*-8*(-9A-B)$	$-B-(-A-(9+8))-(-7654+3+2)+1$
7665	13037	$-1-234-(5+6-789A-B)$	$-BA+98+7654+32+1$
7666	13038	$1*-2*-3*45*(67+8*9-A*B)$	$B+A-9+8+7654-3-2-1$
7667	13039	$1-234+5+6+789A-B$	$-B+A+9+8+7654-3-2*-1$
7668	13040	$1*-2*-34*(-5-(6-(-7-8)))-9*(-A-B)$	$-BA9+8765-4*(32+1)$
7669	13041	$1-(2-3-(-45-6))*(-78-9A-B))$	$-B+A-(-9-(8+7654)-3)-2*1$
766A	13042	$1*2*(-3-(-4567+8*-9*AB))$	$B+A+9-8+7654-3-2+1$
766B	13043	$(-1/-2+3+4^{\wedge}5/6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$-B-(A-9)-(8-(7654+32+1))$
7670	13044	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4-5)*6-7-8*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A-9-8+7654+32*1$
7671	13045	$-1/-2*(-3+(-4-5^{\wedge}6))*(-7-8))/9+A+B$	$BA-(98-7654+3+2*1)$
7672	13046	$1-2+3+(4+5)*-6+7+89*AB$	$B+A-(-9+8)+7654-3-(-2-1)$
7673	13047	$-1-234+5-6+789A+B$	$-B-A-9*-8-(-7654+3+21)$
7674	13048	$12*(3+4+567-(-89-A)+B)$	$B-A+9+8+7654+3+2+1$
7675	13049	$1-234+5-6+789A+B$	$-BA+9-87*(-65-43)+2*-1$
7676	13050	$-1*(234-(-5+6+789A+B))$	$BA-(98-7654)+3-2-1$
7677	13051	$-1+23-45*6*7+89AB$	$BA-98-(7654+3-2)*-1$
7678	13052	$-1*(-23-45*-6*7-89AB)$	$-B-(-A-9-(-8+7654))-(-3+21))$
7679	13053	$1+23-45*6*7+89AB$	$BA-98-(-7654-3*(2-1))$
767A	13054	$-1-234*5+6-7+8*9AB$	$BA-98+7654-(-3-(2-1))$
767B	13055	$1-(2+3+45*6-789A)+B$	$BA-98-(-7654-3*2)-1$
7680	13056	$-1-234-5*-6+789A-B$	$BA-(98-7654)+3-(-2-1)$
7681	13057	$12+34*5+(-6+7+8)*9AB$	$BA-98+7654-3*-2+1$
7682	13058	$12+3*4*(-5+6)*(-78+9*AB)$	$B+A+9+8+7654-3-2+1$
7683	13059	$-1-(234-5)+6+789A+B$	$-B-A-(-9-8)+7654+32+1$
7684	13060	$1-23*4+(56+7-89A)*-B$	$B+A-(-9-8-7654+3)-(-2+1)$
7685	13061	$1-2*-34-(-5-6)*(-7+8-9*-AB)$	$-B+A-9+8+7654-(-32-1)$
7686	13062	$12*(-345+6-(7+8-9AB))$	$B-A-9+8+7654-32*-1$
7687	13063	$-1-(-23-45*-6)+789A-B$	$B-A+9-8+7654+32-1$
7688	13064	$1-23*4-567-89A*-B$	$-BA*(-98+76-54-3-(-2+1))$
7689	13065	$12345-6789-AB$	$B-A+9-8-(-7654-32-1)$
768A	13066	$1+2*3-45*6+789A+B$	$B+A-(9+8)+7654+32*1$
768B	13067	$12+3+4-(-5-6+7+89A)*-B$	$B+A-9-(8-7654-32)+1$
7690	13068	$1*-23*(-4-5-6*(7+8*9))-(-A+B))$	$B*(A+9-(-8-765-(43+21)))$
7691	13069	$1*-2+((3*4-5)^{\wedge}6+7-8)/9+A-B$	$-B-A9-(87*(-65-43)-21)$
7692	13070	$12-3-45*6+789A+B$	$B-A*-987-654-3*(2-1)$
7693	13071	$((-1*2^{\wedge}3-4+5)^{\wedge}6+7-8)/9+A-B$	$-BA9+8*-7*-6*(-5+43-2)*1$
7694	13072	$-1-2*(-3456+7)+8+9AB$	$BA-(98-7654)-(-3-21)$
7695	13073	$-1*-2+((3*4-5)^{\wedge}6+7-8)/9+A-B$	$-BA+98+7654+3*21$
7696	13074	$1-23+4-5-(-6+7+89A)*-B$	$BA-9-8+7654+3*-21$
7697	13075	$1-2+(-3+(-4+5*6)*7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA-9*8+(76-5)*43*(2+1)$
7698	13076	$12+3+45*-6+789A+B$	$B+A-9-8+7^{\wedge}6/(5+4)-3^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
7699	13077	$1234-5*67-8*-9AB$	$-B+A-(-9-(8+7654-(-32+1)))$
769A	13078	$-1-234-(5*-6-789A-B)$	$BA-98-(-7654-(3+21))$
769B	13079	$1234+5678+9AB$	$B-A-(-9-8-7654)-(-32+1)$
76A0	13080	$1-2*-3456*(-7+8)+9AB$	$-B-(A-98-7654-(-32-1))$
76A1	13081	$-12+345*(-6+7-89+AB)$	$-B-A-(-987+65*-4*32+1)$
76A2	13082	$-1-2*345+6+(-7-89A)*-B$	$B-(-A+9)-(-8-7654-32*1)$
76A3	13083	$-1*(23-456-7+8-9)*(A+B)$	$B+A-(9-8)-(-7654-32-1)$
76A4	13084	$1-23-(-4-5+(-6+7+89A)*-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7654-3+21$
76A5	13085	$12345-6*7-89A*B$	$B+A+9-8+7654+32+1$
76A6	13086	$12345-(6789-A*-B)$	$B-A9*-87-6*5*(4+3)+2*-1$
76A7	13087	$1-2-3-4*56+789A-B$	$BA-(98-7654)-(-32+1)$
76A8	13088	$1-(-2-345)+6*(-7-8)*(-9-AB)$	$BA-(98-7654-32*1)$
76A9	13089	$-12-3-456-7-89*-AB$	$BA-98-(-7654-32-1)$
76AA	13090	$12*(3+4-56+78-9A)*-B$	$-B*(-A+9)*(-876-54*32*-1)$
76AB	13091	$-1*-2*(3*((4+5-6)^{\wedge}7-8)+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+98+7654-3-21$
76B0	13092	$-1-234+56+789A-B$	$BA-(-9+8)+7654-3*21$
76B1	13093	$-1*(234-56-789A+B)$	$-BA9+8765+43*-2-1$
76B2	13094	$1-(234-56)+789A-B$	$-BA9+8765-43*-2*-1$
76B3	13095	$-1+2+3+4*-56-(-789A+B)$	$-BA9+8765+43*-2+1$
76B4	13096	$-1+2*3+4*-56+789A-B$	$BA-(-9-8)-(-7*65*-4*3*-2-1)$
76B5	13097	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4-5)*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A9+8-7654+32-1)$
76B6	13098	$1-2*3+(-4+5*6)*-7*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+(-9+8)*(-7654-3*21)$
76B7	13099	$-1-234*5-(-6+7+89+AB)$	$B-(-A-(9+8))+7654-(-32+1)$
76B8	13100	$-1-2-3-456-7+89*AB$	$-B+A-(-98-(7654-32)+1)$
76B9	13101	$1+234*5+6789-(A+B)$	$B-A+9-8-(-7654+3*21)$
76BA	13102	$12-(3-4*-56)-(-789A+B)$	$B-(A-98-7654+32)-1$
76BB	13103	$-12-(3+456)-(-7+89*-AB)$	$B-A+98+7654-32*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7700	13104	$-1^* - 2^* - 3^* 4^* (56^* - 7 - (89 - (A+B)))$	$B - A + 98 - (-7654 + 32) + 1$
7701	13105	$12 + 3^* 4 - (-56 - 789 - A)^* B$	$B - A - (-987 - 65^* - 4^* - 32) + 1$
7702	13106	$-1 - (2 - 3 + 456 + 7) + 89^* AB$	$-B + A9 - 8 + 7654 - 3 - 21$
7703	13107	$-1 - 2 - (3 - 4^* - 56 - (789A + B))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7^* (6 - 5 \wedge 4^* 3 + 2) \wedge 1$
7704	13108	$1 - 2 + 3 - 456 - 7 + 89^* AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4^* (-3 + 21)$
7705	13109	$12 - (-3 + 4) - (5 - (67 - 89A)^* - B)$	$B + A + 9 - (8 + 7 \wedge 6) / (-5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$
7706	13110	$-1 + 2 - (-3 + 456 + 7 + 89^* - AB)$	$BA98 - 76 + 5 - 4321$
7707	13111	$-1234 - 5 - (67 - 89AB)$	$-B + A + 98 + 7654 - 3 - 21$
7708	13112	$-1234 - 56 - 7 + 89AB$	$-B^* (-A + 9)^* (8 + 7 - 6^* - 54^* 3 + 21)$
7709	13113	$-1 - (2 - 3 - (4^* - 56 + 789A + B))$	$-B - A + 98 - (7654 - 3^* 2)^* - 1$
770A	13114	$-1 - (234 - 56 - 789A - B)$	$B - A^* - 9^* (-8 + 76 + 54) - 32 + 1$
770B	13115	$-1^* (234 - 56 - 789A - B)$	$-B + A + 9 + 8 + 7654 - 3^* - 21$
7710	13116	$1 - 234 + 56 + 789A + B$	$B + A - 9^* (8 + 7 - 6^* 5^* (4 + 3) \wedge 2 \wedge 1)$
7711	13117	$12 - 3 - 456 - 7 + 89^* AB$	$B + A9 - (8 - 7654 - (-32 - 1))$
7712	13118	$-123 - (4 + 56^* 7 - 89^* AB)$	$B + A9 - 8 + 7654 + 32^* - 1$
7713	13119	$1 + 2^* 3 + (4 - (5 - 67 + 89A))^* - B$	$-B - A + 98 + 7654 - 3 + 2 + 1$
7714	13120	$1^* - 234^* 5^* (-6 - 7 - 89 - A^* - B)$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 43 - 21$
7715	13121	$-1234 + 5 - 67 + 89AB$	$BA - 9 - 8 + 7654 - (3 + 21)$
7716	13122	$-123 + 4 - 56 + 789A - B$	$B - (-A - 98) + 7654 - (32 + 1)$
7717	13123	$123 - 4 - 567 - 89^* - AB$	$-B - A - (-98 - 7654) - (-3 - 2) - 1$
7718	13124	$12 - 3 - 4^* 56 + 789A + B$	$B - (-A + 9) - 7^* - 654^* (3 - (2 - 1))$
7719	13125	$-123 - (45 + 6) + 789A - B$	$BA - 98 + 7654 + 3^* 21$
771A	13126	$-1234 - 56 + 789AB$	$BA - (9 - 8 - 7654) - 32 - 1$
771B	13127	$-12 - 3 - (4^* - 56 - 78^* (9 + AB))$	$BA - 9 + 8 + 7654 - 32^* 1$
7720	13128	$12345 - 6 + 7 - 89^* A^* B$	$-B + A9 - (8 - 7654) - 3^* - 2^* - 1$
7721	13129	$-1 + 2^* (3 + 4 - 5 - 6 + 7) \wedge 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B + A9 - 8 + 7654 - 3^* 2 + 1$
7722	13130	$-123 + 4 + 56 + (78 + 9)^* AB$	$BA + 9 - 8 + 7654 - (32 - 1)$
7723	13131	$123 + 4 - 567 - 89^* - AB$	$-B + A9 - (8 - 7654 - 3^* (-2 + 1))$
7724	13132	$-12 + 34 + 5 + (67 - 89A)^* - B$	$-B - (-A + 9) - (-7654 + 3 - 2 + 1)$
7725	13133	$-1^* (-2 + 34 - (-567 - 89A^* - B))$	$-B + A + 98 + 7654 - 3 - 2 - 1$
7726	13134	$1 - (-23 + 456) - (7 - 89^* AB)$	$-B + A9 - 8 + 7654 - 3 + 2 + 1$
7727	13135	$-1^* (-2 \wedge 3 + 4 \wedge 5)^* (-6 - 7) - 8^* 9 + A - B$	$B - (A - 98) - (-7654 - (-3 - 2 - 1))$
7728	13136	$1 - 2^* - 3456 + 7^* 8 + 9AB$	$-B + A9 - 8 + 7654 + 3 - (2 - 1)$
7729	13137	$-123 - (45 - 6) - (-789A + B)$	$BA - 9 - (-8 - 7654 + 3 + 21)$
772A	13138	$123 - 4^* 56 - (-78 - 9)^* AB$	$-B - (-A + 9 + 8 - 7654 - 3 - 2 + 1)$
772B	13139	$-1 - 23 - 4 - 567 - 89A^* - B$	$-B + A + 98 + 7654 - 3 + 2 + 1$
7730	13140	$1 + 2^* ((3^* 4 / (5 + 6 - 7)) \wedge 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B + A9 - 8 + 7654 + 3^* - 2^* - 1$
7731	13141	$-1 - 23 + 4 - 56 - (-78 - 9)^* AB$	$-B - A - (-98 - 7654 + 3 - 21)$
7732	13142	$-1 + 2 - 3 + 4^* 56 + 78^* (9 + AB)$	$-BA9 + 8765 - (43 + 2 + 1)$
7733	13143	$12 + 3^* - 4^* 5^* (-6 - 7)^* (8 + 9) - AB$	$BA - 9 - 8 - (-7654 + 3 + 2) - 1$
7734	13144	$-123 + 4 - (56 - 789A - B)$	$B + A9 - (-8 - 7654 + 3 + 21)$
7735	13145	$12 - 34 - (567 - 89A^* B)$	$BA - 9 - 8 + 7654 - (3 + 2 - 1)$
7736	13146	$-1 - 2^* 3^* 4 - 567 + 89A^* B$	$-BA9 + 8765 - (43 - 2 + 1)$
7737	13147	$-1 - 234^* - 5 + 6^* - 7 + 89^* - A^* - B$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 43 + 2^* 1$
7738	13148	$-1234 - 5 - 6^* 7 + 89AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 43 + 2 + 1$
7739	13149	$12 - 3 + 4 - 56^* (-78 - 9A + B)$	$B + A9 - (8 - 7654) + 3^* - 2 - 1$
773A	13150	$-123 - 456 - 7 + 89A^* B$	$B + A9 + 8 + 7654 + 3 - 21$
773B	13151	$-1 + 2 - 3^* - 456 + 78^* (-9 + AB)$	$B + A9 - (8 - 7654 + 3^* 2 - 1)$
7740	13152	$1 - (-2 - (3 - 4 \wedge 5 / -6) - 7)^* - 8^* - 9 + A - B$	$B - (-A + 9) - (-7654 + 3 + 2 - 1)$
7741	13153	$(-1^* (-2 - 3) + 4 \wedge 5 / 6 + 7)^* 8^* 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA9 - (-8765 + 4 + 32) - 1$
7742	13154	$1234 + 56^* - 7 + 89^* A^* B$	$-BA9 + 8765 - (4 + 32^* 1)$
7743	13155	$12 + 3456 + 7^* (-89A + B)^* - B$	$BA - 9 - (8 - 7654) - (-3 - 2 - 1)$
7744	13156	$-12 + 3 - 4 - 567 + 89A^* B$	$B + A9 - 8 + 7654 - 3 + 2 + 1$
7745	13157	$-12 - 34^* 5 - (6 - 789A) + B$	$-B - A + 98 + 7654 + 32^* 1$
7746	13158	$-123 + 4 - 5^* 6 - (-789A + B)$	$-B - A + 98 + 7654 + 32 + 1$
7747	13159	$-123 - 45 + 6 + 789A + B$	$BA - (9 - 8 - 7654 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
7748	13160	$12^* (-3 - (-4 + 5) - (-678 - (9 - A - B)))$	$BA - 9 + 8 + 7654 + 3^* - 2 + 1$
7749	13161	$-1^* (2 + 34 - 5 - (6 - 78))^* (-9A + B)$	$B + A + 98 - (-7654 - 3 + 2) - 1$
774A	13162	$1 - ((-2^* - 3 - 4 \wedge 5)^* (6 + 7) + 8^* 9) + A - B$	$-B - (-A + 9 + 8 - 7654 - 3 - 21)$
774B	13163	$-1^* (-2^* - 3 - 4 \wedge 5)^* (6 + 7) - 8^* 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA9 + 8765 + 4 - 32 + 1$
7750	13164	$-123 - 456 + 7 + 89A^* B$	$BA - 9 - (8 - 765^* 4^* 3) + 2 + 1$
7751	13165	$1^* 234 - (-5 + 6 + (7 - 89)^* AB)$	$B + A9 - (8 - 7654) - (-3 + 2 + 1)$
7752	13166	$123 + 456 + (-789 - A)^* - B$	$B + A - (-98 - 7654) - (-3 - 2^* 1)$
7753	13167	$-1^* (-23 - 45 + 6 - 789 - A)^* B$	$-B + A + 98 + 7654 + 3 + 21$
7754	13168	$1^* - 2 + 3 - 4 - 567 + 89A^* B$	$-B - (A9 - 8) + 7^* (-65 + 4 - 3)^* - 21$
7755	13169	$-123 - 4 - 5 - (6 - 789A + B)$	$B - A + 98 + 7654 + 3 + 21$
7756	13170	$-1 - 2^* - 3456 - (-78 - 9AB)$	$-BA9 + 8765 - (43 - 21)$
7757	13171	$1^* (-2 - 3 + 4)^* (567 - 89A^* B)$	$BA + 9 - 8 - (-7654 - 3) - (-2 + 1)$
7758	13172	$-1234 + 5^* - 6 + 7 + 89AB$	$-B + A9 - (-8 - 7654) - (3 - 21)$
7759	13173	$-12 + 3 - 45 + 6 - (-78 - 9)^* AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4^* 3^* 2 + 1$
775A	13174	$1234 + 5 - 6 - (-789A + B)$	$B + A9 + 8 - (-7654 - 3 + 2) + 1$
775B	13175	$12345 - 6789 - A - B$	$B - A - 9 - 87^* (-65 - 43) - 2 + 1$
7760	13176	$-1^* - 2^* (34 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 8)^* (-9 + AB)$	$B + A9 + 8 - (-7654 - (3 + 2) + 1)$
7761	13177	$-123 + 4 - 5 - 6 + 789A - B$	$BA - 9 - 8 + 7654 + 3 + 21$
7762	13178	$12 - 3 - 4 - 567 - 89A^* - B$	$-BA9 + 8765 - (-4 - 3) - 21$
7763	13179	$-123 - 4 + 5 - 6 - (-789A + B)$	$B - (A - 98 - (7654 + 32^* 1))$
7764	13180	$-123 - (-4 - 5^* - 6 - 789A) + B$	$B - (A - 98) - (-7654 - 32 - 1)$
7765	13181	$-123 - 4 - 5 - (-6 - 789A + B)$	$-B + A9 + 87 - 65 + 4 - (-3 + 21)$
7766	13182	$12 - 3^* - 4 + (5 - 67 + 89A)^* B$	$BA - (-9 - 8 - 7654) - (3 + 2^* - 1)$
7767	13183	$12 - 3^* (-4 + 56) - (-789A + B)$	$BA + 9 - (-8 - 7654 - 3) - (2 + 1)$
7768	13184	$-1 - 2 + 3 - 45 + 6 + (78 + 9)^* AB$	$-B + A98^* 7 - (6^* - 54^* - 3^* - 2 + 1)$
7769	13185	$12 - 34^* 5 - (6 - 789A) + B$	$-BA9 - (-8765 + 4 - 3^* - 2 + 1)$
776A	13186	$-1 - 2 + 3^* - 4 - 5^* 6 - (-78 - 9)^* AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
776B	13187	$-1234 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89AB$	$BA98 - 7 - 6 + 5 - 4321$
7770	13188	$-1 - 2 - 345 - 67 - 89^* - AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
7771	13189	$1^* - 2 - (345 + 67) - 89^* - AB$	$-B + A^* (-9 + 8 - 7)^* (6 - (54 - 3))^* (2 + 1)$
7772	13190	$-1234 - 5 - (6 - 7)^* 89AB$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 + 2 - 1$
7773	13191	$1 + 234^* 5 + (6 - 7)^* - 89^* A^* B$	$-BA9 + 876^* (-5 - 4 + 3)^* 2^* - 1$
7774	13192	$12 + 3 + 4 - 567 + 89A^* B$	$-BA9 - (-8765 + 4) - 3 + 2 + 1$
7775	13193	$-1 - 2 + 34 + (5 - (67 - 89A))^* B$	$BA + 9^* (8765) + 4^* 321$
7776	13194	$1^* (-2 - 3 - 4)^* (-5 + 6^* - 7 + 8 - 9AB)$	$-BA9 + 8765 - 4 - (-3 + 2) + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7777	13195	12345-6789+A-B	BA+9-(8-(7654+3)-21)
7778	13196	12345+6789*(A-B)	-BA9+8765+4-3-2+1
7779	13197	12345-6789-A+B	-BA9+8765+4+3*(-2+1)
777A	13198	1234-5+6-789*-A+B	-BA9+8765-(-4+3-2+1)
777B	13199	-123+4-5-6-(-789A-B)	-BA9+8765+4-3+2*1
7780	13200	-1234+5+(-6+7)*89AB	B*A*(98+76-54-(-3+21))
7781	13201	-123-(4-5+6-789A-B)	BA98-(-7+6)+5-4321
7782	13202	-1+23*-4-56+789A+B	-BA9+8765+4+3-2+1
7783	13203	-1234-(5-6)-(-7-89AB)	BA98-(-7-6+5+4321)
7784	13204	1-2+34-56+(-78-9)*-AB	BA-(9-8-7654)-(-32-1)
7785	13205	12-(345+67)+89*AB	-BA9+8765-(-4-3+2*-1)
7786	13206	(1-(2-3+4)^5+6)*-7*8-9+A-B	BA*(-98+76-54-3)*(-2+1)
7787	13207	12+3*(4+5)*-6+789A-B	BA+98+7654+3*-21
7788	13208	123-45*6+789A-B	BA+98+7*(-654+3)*-2*1
7789	13209	-123+4-(-5+6-789A-B)	-B+A9-8+7654+3*21
778A	13210	1-2+34-567+89A*B	-BA9+8765-(-4*3-2*1)
778B	13211	1234+5*-67-89*-A*B	B+A9+8+7654+32+1
7790	13212	1-23-4+5+6+(-78-9)*-AB	BA9+87-65*4*(-32+1)
7791	13213	-123-4+5+6+789A+B	BA98+7+6-(-5+4321)
7792	13214	1+2+34-(567+89A*-B)	BA-9+8765-4*321
7793	13215	-1+2+3*(-45+6)+789A-B	B+A+987*6+54*3*21
7794	13216	-1-234-5*6*7+89*AB	B-A9*-87-(65+4-(-3+2))*1
7795	13217	12345-6789+A+B	-B-(-A-9)-(87*(-65-43)-21)
7796	13218	-123+4+5*6+789A-B	BA98-7+6*5-4321
7797	13219	12345+6*-7+8*-9AB	-BA9+8765-(4*3*-2+1)
7798	13220	-123-4*-5-6+789A+B	-BA9-(-8765-(-4+3)-21)
7799	13221	-123+4+5-(-6-789A-B)	B+A9+8765+4*-321
779A	13222	-12-3*-4*(5-(-6-789A)-B)	-BA9+8765+4-3+21
779B	13223	-1-23-456+(-7+89A)*B	-BA-98-(-7654-321)
77A0	13224	1234-56-78*(9-AB)	-B+A9*87-(6+5)-(-4-(-32+1))
77A1	13225	12-(-34+567+89A*-B)	-B+A9+8+7654+3*21
77A2	13226	12-3*45-6+789A+B	B-A9*-87-6*5-(4-32*-1)
77A3	13227	-123+4*56*7-89*A*-B	-B-A*-987-6-543+21
77A4	13228	-1+2-(-3-4)-5-(6-(78+9)*AB)	-BA9-(-8765-4)-(-3-21)
77A5	13229	-1+2*(-34-5)*(-6+7-(8+9+AB))	-BA9+8765-4+32-1
77A6	13230	123-45*6+789A+B	-BA9+8765-(4-32*1)
77A7	13231	-123+45-6+789A-B	-BA9-(-8765+4-32)+1
77A8	13232	-1234-5*-6+7+89AB	BA+9+8765-4*321
77A9	13233	1*(2-(3+45+6+7-89A))*B	B-A*-987+6-543-2-1
77AA	13234	-123-456-(7+89A)*-B	B+A*987-(6-543-2)*-1
77AB	13235	-12-34-56-(-789A+B)	B+A+9*(-8*7+6*(5+4/3)^(2+1))
77B0	13236	-1*(2+3-4^5*(6+7))-8*9-(A-B)	B+A+98+7654-3*-21
77B1	13237	1-2-(-3+4*-5*-6)-(-789A+B)	-BA9-(-8765-4-32+1)
77B2	13238	1-23+4*-56*-7-8*-9AB	-BA9+8765-(-4-32*1)
77B3	13239	1234+567+8*9*A*B	B-A9*-87-6-5-43+2+1
77B4	13240	1+23*-4-5*6-(-789A-B)	BA-9+8+7654-3*-21
77B5	13241	1-2-3*-4+5-6-(-78-9)*AB	B+A*(987-6-(54+3)-(-2+1))
77B6	13242	1-2-(3-(4+5))+6-(78+9)*-AB	BA+9-8-(-7654+3*-21)
77B7	13243	1+23*4-56*(78-9A+B)	BA-(-98-7654)-32-1
77B8	13244	-1234-(-56+7)+89AB	-BA9+8765+43-2-1
77B9	13245	-1*(-2*3-4^5*(6+7))+8*9)+A-B	BA+98+7654-32+1
77BA	13246	-123-4+56+789A-B	-BA9+8765+43-(2-1)
77BB	13247	12+3*(-456-7-89*-A)*B	B+A9*87-(65-43+21)
7800	13248	12345-6-7-8*9AB	-BA9+8765-(-43-2+1)
7801	13249	1-2*(3+4+5-6)*7*(89-A-B))	-BA9+8765+43-2*-1
7802	13250	-1+2-34-56+789A-B	-BA9+8765+43+2+1
7803	13251	1234+56+789*A-B	-B-A9*-87-65+43-(-2+1)
7804	13252	1+2-34-(56-789A)-B	-B-A9*-87-(65-43)+2*1
7805	13253	-123+45-6+789A+B	BA+98+765*4*3-21
7806	13254	-123+4+56-(-789A+B)	BA+98+7654-3-21
7807	13255	-12-345+6-7-89*-AB	-B+A9*87+6-(54-(32-1))
7808	13256	1-2-(345+6)-(-7+89*-AB)	-B+A98+7+65*-4*-32*1
7809	13257	-12-34-56-(-789A-B)	B+A9*87-6*-5+4-3*21
780A	13258	-1*(23+4+56-789A+B)	-B+A9*87-(6-(5+4)-3)*(-2-1)
780B	13259	1-(23+4)-(56-789A+B)	-B-A*(-987+65-4-3+2*1)
7810	13260	12345+6-7-8*9AB	BA+98+7654-(-3+21)
7811	13261	-1-23-(4-56*-7)-89*-AB	B-A*-987+6-543+21
7812	13262	12345+6+7-8*9AB	B+A+(-9-8)*-7+6/((-5-4)^-3/((-2-1))
7813	13263	1-(23+4)-(56*7-89*AB)	-B-A9*-87-6+5+4*3*(-2+1)
7814	13264	-12-3+45*(-6-7)-89A*-B	-B+A9*87+6*5-4+32*-1
7815	13265	-1-(23-4+56-789A+B)	BA98-(7-65)-4321
7816	13266	1*-23-(-4+56-(789A-B))	-B*(-A9+8-765-(-4+3)-2+1)
7817	13267	1-23+4-56+789A-B	-BA9+8765-4-3*-21
7818	13268	-123-4+56-(-789A-B)	B+A9*87+6-(-5+4+32-1)
7819	13269	-1234-5-(-67-89AB)	-B+A*(9+876)-(-543+2)+1
781A	13270	1-23-45-6+789A-B	B-A9*-87-65+43-2*1
781B	13271	12-(345+6+7-89*AB)	B+A*(987-6*-5+43*-2-1)
7820	13272	-12-3-(4+56*7)+89*AB	-BA9+8765+43+21
7821	13273	1234+56-(789*-A-B)	B+A9*87-65+43+2-1
7822	13274	1-(-23-4)+5+6-(78+9)*-AB	BA98+76*(-5-43-21)
7823	13275	1+234+56-78*(-9-AB)	-B-A9*-87-65+43+21
7824	13276	-12-(3-4)-56-(-789A+B)	BA+98-765*-4*3+2*-1
7825	13277	123-456-7-89*-AB	BA+98-(-7654+3-2*-1)
7826	13278	-1+2*(-34+5)-6+789A-B	BA-(-98-7654+3+2)+1
7827	13279	-1234-(-5-67)+89AB	BA98+7+65-4321
7828	13280	-1-23-(45-6-789A+B)	BA98+76-5-4321
7829	13281	1-(23+4+56-789A-B)	-B+A9*87-6+5-(-4-3)-2+1
782A	13282	-12+3+4-56+789A-B	BA+98-(-7654+3)+2+1
782B	13283	-1+234-567-89*-AB	B+A9*87-(-6-(5-(43-21)))
7830	13284	123-4*56+789A+B	BA+98+7654-(-3+2)+1
7831	13285	12-34-56+789A+B	BA-(-98-7654)-3*(-2+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7832	13286	$1 - (-2 - (-345+6) - (7+89*AB))$	$BA+98 - (-7654-3-2+1)$
7833	13287	$-12-3^*-4-56+789A-B$	$BA+98 - (-7654-3) - 2^*-1$
7834	13288	$1+2^*-3 - (-4+56) - (-789A+B)$	$BA+98 - (-7654-3)+2+1$
7835	13289	$1 - (2+3-4+56-789A+B)$	$BA+98+7654-3^*-2+1$
7836	13290	$-12-3-(4-(-56-(-789A-B)))$	$BA98+76+5-4321$
7837	13291	$-12-3-(45-6-(789A-B))$	$B+A9^*87-6-5+4^*(3-2)^*1$
7838	13292	$1-23-(45+6-789A-B)$	$B-A^*(-987-6)-543+2^*1$
7839	13293	$1-2-3+4+56^*-7+89^*AB$	$BA+98-7^*(654+3)^*-2+1$
783A	13294	$-1+2-3-45-6+789A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7^*(6+5^4))/3-2^*1$
783B	13295	$1+2345-(67-8^*9^*AB)$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7^*6)^*(-5+4^3)/2-1$
7840	13296	$-1-2+3-(45-(-6+789A-B))$	$-B+A9^*87-6+54-32^*1$
7841	13297	$-1+2+3+4-56+789A-B$	$B+A9^*87-65+43+21$
7842	13298	$-12-3+4-(-56-789A)+B$	$B-A9^*-87-654^*(-3+2+1)$
7843	13299	$1+2+3+4-(-56-789A)+B$	$B^*(-A9+876-(5+43^*2+1))$
7844	13300	$12-3-4+56^*-7-89^*-AB$	$-B-A987-(6+54)^*-321$
7845	13301	$-12-3-45-6+789A+B$	$-B+A9^*87+65-43-2+1$
7846	13302	$-1-23-(45-6-789A-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*7^*(6+(-5-4)^3/(2+1))$
7847	13303	$12+3^*-4^*5-6-(-789A+B)$	$B-A9^*-87+6-(5-4-3-(-2-1))$
7848	13304	$1-(23+45)+6-(-789A-B)$	$BA+98-(-7654+3-21)$
7849	13305	$-1+2-3-(4+56)-(-789A-B)$	$B+A9^*87-6+5-(-4-(3+2-1))$
784A	13306	$12345-(6789-A^*B)$	$B-A9^*(-8-76-5)+4+3+2-1$
784B	13307	$-1-2+3-(4+56-789A-B)$	$-B+A9^*87-(6-5-4-3)+21$
7850	13308	$1^*(-2+3)^*-45+6+789A-B$	$-BA9+8765-4^*(-3-21)$
7851	13309	$1-2+3-4-(-56-789A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-98-(-7-65+4))^*(-32+1)$
7852	13310	$12-(3-4+56-789A)-B$	$B^*(A+9-(876+5)-4-3+2+1)$
7853	13311	$-1+2^*-3-(45+6)-(-789A-B)$	$B-A^*-987-(65+43-21)$
7854	13312	$-1+2+3-45+6+789A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*-7/-6-(5+4)^3)^*2+1$
7855	13313	$1-(-2-3+4)-(-56-789A-B)$	$B-A9^*-87-(6+5)-(-43+21)$
7856	13314	$1+2+3-45-(-6-789A)+B$	$BA9-87-65^*-4^*-32^*-1$
7857	13315	$-1-2+3^*-456-(7-89AB)$	$-B+A9^*87+(-6-5^*-4)^*3-2-1$
7858	13316	$-1+2-3-45-6+789A+B$	$-B-A+9^*8-7^*((-6-5^4)^*3-2^*1)$
7859	13317	$1-2-(3+456-(-7+89A^*B))$	$-B-A+9^*(8+(-7-6^*-5)^4+3+2)^*1$
785A	13318	$12-34-5-(6-789A)+B$	$-B+A9^*87+(-6+5)^*(-4-32)^*1$
785B	13319	$12-3-(45-6-789A)+B$	$BA-(-98-7654-32+1)$
7860	13320	$-1^*(-2-3-(4-56+789A+B))$	$BA+98-(-7654-32)^*1$
7861	13321	$-12+3^*456-7-8^*-9AB$	$BA+98-(-7654-32)+1$
7862	13322	$-1+2+3-45-6+789A+B$	$-B-A9^*87+6^*(5+4)^*32+1$
7863	13323	$1-2-(-3+456+7)-89A^*-B$	$B+A9-87^*(-65-43)-2+1$
7864	13324	$12+3-4-56+789A+B$	$-B-A9^*-87+6+54+3-21$
7865	13325	$1-2-34-(-5+6)+789A+B$	$B-A-98+7^*-6^*54^*(3+2)^*-1$
7866	13326	$12-(3-(4-56))-(-789A-B)$	$-B+A9^*87-6+5+43^*(2-1)$
7867	13327	$12345-6789+AB$	$-B+A9^*87-(-65+43-21)$
7868	13328	$-1+2-3-45+6+789A+B$	$-B^*-A-9^*(8-7^*(6+5^4)+3)/(2+1)$
7869	13329	$1+2-34+5+6+789A-B$	$-B+A9^*87-(-6+5-43-2+1)$
786A	13330	$12-(34+5-6)-(-789A+B)$	$B+A9^*87+(6-5)^*4+3+2+1$
786B	13331	$1^*2+34-56-(-789A+B)$	$B-A^*9^*(-87-(65-(4+3)-21))$
7870	13332	$1^*-2^*3^*(-4-567+8-9AB)$	$B^*(A+9+876+5-43-2-1)$
7871	13333	$-1+2-3^*456+7+89AB$	$-B-A9-8+7654+321$
7872	13334	$-1+23-(45-6-789A)+B$	$-B+A9^*-8^*(-7-6)+5-43-21$
7873	13335	$-12-345+67-89^*-AB$	$BA-(987+6^*54^*-32^*1)$
7874	13336	$1+23-45+6-(-789A)+B$	$BA-987+6^*54^*32+1$
7875	13337	$-12+34-56+789A+B$	$B+A-9+(8^*(7-6)+5)^*(4^*(3+2)+1)$
7876	13338	$123-4-(567+89A^*-B)$	$-BA-9+8+7654+321$
7877	13339	$-1+2-34-5+6+789A+B$	$-BA-98+7+6^*5^*(-4+321)$
7878	13340	$12-34-5-(6-789A)+B$	$-BA-(-9+8)+7654+321$
7879	13341	$-12-3-(-4-(5-6+789A-B))$	$B-A9^*-87+(-65-4+32)^*-1$
787A	13342	$-1-2-3+4-5-6+789A-B$	$-B-A9^*-87+(-6-5-4)^*(3-21)$
787B	13343	$1+23+4-56+789A+B$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(876+5+4-32)^*-1$
7880	13344	$1-23+4-5-6+789A+B$	$-B-A-(98-(7654+321))$
7881	13345	$-1-2-3+4-5+6+789A+B$	$B+A+9^*8+7^*(6+5^4)^*3+2-1$
7882	13346	$-1+2^*(-3-4-5)-6-(-789A-B)$	$B+A+9^*8-7^*(-6-5^4)^*3+2^1$
7883	13347	$12+3-45+6+789A+B$	$-BA9+8765+4^*32-1$
7884	13348	$-1+2^*3^*4+5^*-6+789A-B$	$BA^*(987-6^*5+43^*-21)$
7885	13349	$-12-(-3-4)-(-5-6)+789A-B$	$-B-A9+8-(-7654-321)$
7886	13350	$1+2-3-(4-5)-(-6-789A)+B$	$B+A-9-(-8-7^*(6+5^4+3))^*(2+1)$
7887	13351	$-12+3-4-5-6+789A+B$	$-B+A9^*87+65+4-3-2-1$
7888	13352	$-1-(-2-34)-(-56-789A-B)$	$-B+A^*(-98-7)-6^*-54^*32+1$
7889	13353	$-12-3-(-4-(5+6+789A))-B$	$-B+A9^*87-(-6+5-43-21)$
788A	13354	$-12+3^*4-5+6+789A-B$	$-B^*(A-(9+876-54+32-1))$
788B	13355	$1-(234+56+7-89^*AB)$	$B-(A9+8)-(-7654-321)$
7890	13356	$1^*23+4^*-5-6+789A-B$	$-BA-(-9-8)-(-7654-321)$
7891	13357	$-1^*(-23+45-(6-(-789A-B)))$	$BA-(-98-7654)+3^*21$
7892	13358	$-1-(2-3)-(-4-5+6-789A)-B$	$B+A+9^*8-7^*((-6-5^4)^*3-2^*1)$
7893	13359	$12-3+4-(5+6)-(-789A)+B$	$B+A+9^*(8+(-7-6^*-5)^4+3+2)^*1$
7894	13360	$-1+2-(-3+4)-5-6+789A+B$	$B+A-9-8-7^*6^*(-5^*4+3+2)^*1$
7895	13361	$1+2^*-3+4-(-5+6+789)^*-AB$	$B+A+(9^*8^*(7+6^*5)+4)^*(3+2^1)$
7896	13362	$12-(34-5-6-789A-B)$	$-B-A^*(-987-6+54)-32+1$
7897	13363	$1-(-23+456)+7-89A^*-B$	$B+A9^*87-6-(5-43)+21$
7898	13364	$1-2+3-4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B-(-A-(-98+7654+321))$
7899	13365	$1-23-4^*-5-6+789A+B$	$B^*(-A9-(-876-54-32))^*1$
789A	13366	$-1+2+34-5^*6-(-789A)+B$	$-B-A9^*-87+65+4-3^*(-2-1)$
789B	13367	$-12-(34-56)-(-789A)+B$	$B+A+(-9+(8+7/6)^*(5+4)^3)^*2-1$
78A0	13368	$-1-(-2+3)-(-4-5)+6+789A-B$	$-B+A9^*-8^*(-7-6)-5-4-3-21$
78A1	13369	$12-(3-4-5)-(-6-789A)+B$	$-BA+98^*76-5^*-432+1$
78A2	13370	$1+2^*34-56+789A-B$	$B+A^*(-98+7+6+543)^*2-1$
78A3	13371	$1+23-4-5^*6+789A+B$	$B-A9+8+7654+321$
78A4	13372	$-1-2^*-34+56^*-7-89^*-AB$	$B-A9^*-87+6+54+3-(-2+1)$
78A5	13373	$12-3-4-5-6-(-789A-B)$	$B-A9^*-87-65+4^*32^*1$
78A6	13374	$-1-2+3-4-5+6+789A+B$	$B+A-9^*8-7^*(-6^*-5/-4^*-3+2)-1$
78A7	13375	$1+2+3-4^*-5-(-6-789A)+B$	$B-A9^*-87+6+54-3^*-2+1$
78A8	13376	$1-(-23-4+5+6-789A)-B$	$-B^*(A9-876-54-32-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
78A9	13377	$1-23-4^*5+6+789A+B$	$-B+A9^*87+6^*5-4+3^*21$
78AA	13378	$-1-2-(34-56)-(-789A+B)$	$-B-(A-9)-87^*(-65-(43+2))^*1$
78AB	13379	$-1-2^*-3^*4-5-(-6-789A)-B$	$-B-A9^*-87+65+4-3+21$
78B0	13380	$-12+34+5-6+789A-B$	$B+A-98-7^*65^*(4-3)^*-21$
78B1	13381	$12-(3-(4-5)+6-789A-B)$	$B-A^*(-987-6-(-54-3))-(-2+1))$
78B2	13382	$-1^*(2-3)^*4-5+6+789A+B$	$-B^*-A+(-9^*-8+7)^*-6^*(5-4^3/2-1)$
78B3	13383	$1-2+34-5-6-(-789A+B)$	$B+A^*(987-65)+4^*32^*1$
78B4	13384	$12^*(34-56+789-AB)$	$-B+A9^*87-(-6-54-32)^*1$
78B5	13385	$-12-3-(-45-(-6+789A)+B)$	$B+A+(9+(8-7)/6)^*(5+4)^3*2-1$
78B6	13386	$-12-3-(4^*-56^*-7-89AB)$	$B+A^*987-(-6-5)+432^*-1$
78B7	13387	$1+2+34-(5+6-789A)-B$	$-B+A9^*87-(-65+4+32^*-1)$
78B8	13388	$1-2^*(-3+45+6^*-789)+AB$	$-B-A^*9+8+7654+321$
78B9	13389	$-1-23-(4-56-(789A-B))$	$BA+9^*-8^*(-76+5-4-3)^*2-1$
78BA	13390	$1+23-4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B+A9^*87+65+4^*3+21$
78BB	13391	$-12+3+45-(-6-789A+B)$	$-B+A+9^*(87-(-654-321))$
7900	13392	$12+3^*4+5-(-6-789A+B)$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2+1$
7901	13393	$-1-2-(-34-(-5-(-6-789A)-B))$	$-B-A9^*-87-6^*.5^*4-3^*(2-1)$
7902	13394	$1+2-(-3+45-67^*(8+9)^*A)+B$	$BA9-8^*7^*-65+4321$
7903	13395	$12-34+56+789A-B$	$-B-A^*-987+6^*5-432^*1$
7904	13396	$-1-(23-45+6-789A)+B$	$B+A^*9^*(-8-(-76-54-3))-21$
7905	13397	$1-(-2-34)-(-5+6)-(-789A+B)$	$B-A^*-987-(-6-5+432+1)$
7906	13398	$12+34-(5+6-789A)-B$	$-B^*(-A+9-876+54-32-1)$
7907	13399	$1-23-(-4-56-(789A-B))$	$B+A+(-9+8-7^*.6^*5)^*4^3+2/1$
7908	13400	$-12-(3+4-56-(789A-B))$	$B+A9^*-8^*(-7-6)-54-(-32+1)$
7909	13401	$1234-5-(-6789+AB)$	$BA9-8-7-65^*-4^*32-1$
790A	13402	$1+2-3+4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B-A98-7-6^*.54^*(32+1)$
790B	13403	$-12+3-(-45-6-789A+B)$	$-B-A9^*(-8-76)+543+2-1$
7910	13404	$-12+34-5+6+789A+B$	$B+A-9^*8+(7-6^*5^*4-3)^2-1$
7911	13405	$1-2-(-3+4-5^*6-(789A+B))$	$BA+9^*-8+7^*(65-4^*-321)$
7912	13406	$-12+3-4+56+789A-B$	$B-A9^*-87-(-6-54-32^*1)$
7913	13407	$-12-3+45-(6-(789A+B))$	$B-A9^*-87+65-(-4-3)+21$
7914	13408	$-1-23+45+6+789A+B$	$-B+A-(-9^*-8-7654)+321$
7915	13409	$1+2-(-34-5-6-789A+B)$	$-B^*(A+98+7-65-43^*21)$
7916	13410	$1+23-(-4-(-5+6+789A)-B)$	$B-A-9^*8-(-7654-321)$
7917	13411	$1234+5+6789-AB$	$-BA+9^*8+7654+321$
7918	13412	$1^*-23-4-(-56-789A-B)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7^*-6^*5-4^*3^*2)-1$
7919	13413	$-12+3+45-6+789A+B$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7^*6^*5-4^*3^*2)^1$
791A	13414	$-1-2+3+4+5+6-(-789A+B)$	$-B+A^*-98-7+6^*54^*32^*1$
791B	13415	$1-(2-34-5)-6+789A+B$	$BA9-8+7-65^*-4^*32-1$
7920	13416	$1-(2-(3+4+5+6))-(-789A+B)$	$-B-(A98-7-6^*.54^*(32-1))$
7921	13417	$12-34-(-56-789A)-B$	$-B-A+9-8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2-1$
7922	13418	$-1+2+3+4+5-(-6-(789A-B))$	$-B+A987+6^*-5^*(4+3)^*21$
7923	13419	$-12+3^*4-(-56-789A+B)$	$-BA-987^*(6-5)-4^*321$
7924	13420	$12-(-34-(-5-6+789A))+B$	$B^*A^*(98-7^*6-5^*-4+3+21)$
7925	13421	$1+2+34-(5-6-(789A+B))$	$-B-A9^*-87+6+54-3^*-21$
7926	13422	$1^*2+3-4+5+6+789A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(-7^*.6^*5^*-4+3)^*-2^*1$
7927	13423	$-1+2-3+4-(-56-789A+B)$	$BA+987+(-6-5^*4)^*-321$
7928	13424	$1-2^*-3-4-(-56-789A)-B$	$-B+A9^*87+65-4-3^*-21$
7929	13425	$1+2-3+4+5+6+789A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*-8-7^*(-6-5^*4+3))^*(2+1)$
792A	13426	$12^*(3-(-4-5^*-6-789+AB))$	$-B-A-9+(8-7-6^*5^*4+3)^2/1$
792B	13427	$-1+2^*3^*4-(-567-8-9AB))$	$-B+A98-(76-54)^*-321$
7930	13428	$12+3+4+5+6+789A+B$	$-BA-9-876^*-5+4321$
7931	13429	$-12-34+5+6^*-7+89A^*B$	$B+A-9-(8-(-7^*(-6^*-5^*-4^3+2)-1))$
7932	13430	$1+23+45-(-6-789A+B)$	$B+A-9-8+7^*(6^*5^*4^3+2)^1$
7933	13431	$-12+3-4+5+67^*(8+9)^*A+B$	$B^*(A-9)^*(876-(-5+4)+3-21)$
7934	13432	$1-2-3+4+5+6+789A+B$	$B+A9^*87-(6+5)^*-4^*3-2^*-1$
7935	13433	$-1-2-(-3-(-4+56))-(-789A+B))$	$-B-A+9+8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2-1$
7936	13434	$-1+2-3+4+5+6+789A+B$	$B+A-(-9-8)^*((-7-6)^*5^*-4+3)^*(2+1)$
7937	13435	$1+234^*(5-6)+7+89^*AB$	$-BA-987+6^*-54^*(-32-1)$
7938	13436	$1-2-3-4^*5^*-6^*(-7-89)^*(A-B)$	$B-A^*98-7+6^*.54^*32^*-1$
7939	13437	$-12-34-(5+67^*(8+9))^*-A+B$	$B+A^*987+65^*(-4-3)-21$
793A	13438	$1-2+3+4+5+6+789A+B$	$B+A+(-9-(-8^*-7^*.6^*5^*4+3))^*2+1$
793B	13439	$1-(-23-(4+5^*6)-789A-B)$	$-B-(A9-876^*5-4321)$
7940	13440	$12^*(-3-(-4+5))-(-678-9-A+B))$	$B+A987+6^*5^*(4+3)^*-21$
7941	13441	$12+3+4+5-6+789A+B$	$-B-A^*-987+65-432-1$
7942	13442	$1+23+45-(-6-789A+B)$	$-B+A+9^*876+5^*(-4+321)$
7943	13443	$-1+23-4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B-(A+9)-(8-7654-321)$
7944	13444	$-1+2+3^*-4^*-5-(-6-789A-B)$	$B+A-9-(8-7^*6^*5^*4^3)^2(2-1)$
7945	13445	$-1+2^*34-(5+6-789A)-B$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2-1$
7946	13446	$1-(234-5-6)+7+89^*AB$	$-BA+9-(-876^*5-4321)$
7947	13447	$-1-(23-4^*-5^*-6)-(-789A+B)$	$-B-A9^*8^*(-7-6)-(-54-3+21)$
7948	13448	$-123+45^*67-8^*-9^*AB$	$B-A^*(-987-6+54-3)-2-1$
7949	13449	$1-2+3+4-(-56-789A-B)$	$-B-A^*(-987+65-(-4+3+21))$
794A	13450	$12-3-4+5+6+789A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*-7^*-6^*-5^*4+3)^*2+1$
794B	13451	$-1-234^*(-5-6)-78^*(-9A+B)$	$-B-A9+8^*(765+432)-1$
7950	13452	$-123-45-67-89^*-AB$	$-B-A9-8^*(-765-432)^*1$
7951	13453	$1+23+4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B-(A9+8^*(-765-432))^+1$
7952	13454	$1234-5-(6+7+8^*-9AB)$	$-B-A+(-9^*(-8+7^*-6)^*-5+4)^*-3^*2-1$
7953	13455	$1-2+3^*4+5+6^*7+89-AB$	$-BA+98+7654+321$
7954	13456	$123-4-5+6+789A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-(6+5+4)^3/2)^1$
7955	13457	$-1234-56-7^*(-8-9)^*AB$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2-1$
7956	13458	$-1-(2-34)+56-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^*5^*4^3+2^1$
7957	13459	$12345+6-78^*(-9+AB)$	$-B-A-(9-8-7654-321)$
7958	13460	$1-2+3+4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B+A^*(-9+8)+7654+321$
7959	13461	$12-(-34+5^*6)-(-789A-B)$	$-B-A^*(-987+6)-(-5-4+321)$
795A	13462	$-1-(-2-34-56)-(-789A+B)$	$-BA-98-7^*(6+54)^*(-3-21)$
795B	13463	$1^*23-(-45-6-789A)+B$	$-B+A-9-8-(-7654-321)$
7960	13464	$12+3+4+5+6-(-789A-B)$	$-B^*(-A9-(-87-65))^*(4-3-21)$
7961	13465	$12+34-5+(6+7)^*8^*(9A+B)$	$B-A-9-(8-7654)+321$
7962	13466	$1^*23-4-(-56-789A)-B$	$B-A9+8^*(765+432-1)$
7963	13467	$123-(45+6)-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9+(8-7-6^*5^*4+3)^2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7964	13468	1234-5-6-(-7+8*-9AB)	B+A-9+(8-7-6*5*4+3)^2/1
7965	13469	-12-(-34-56)-(-789A-B)	-BA+9*876-54*-32+1
7966	13470	1*2*3*(-4-5+678+9A*B)	-B+A*987+6+5*(-43*2-1)
7967	13471	1-2-(345+6+7)+89A*B	B+A+9+8*7*6*5*4^(3/2)+1
7968	13472	1+23-45*6+7-89*-AB	B+A-9*8-7*-6*(-5*-4^3+2)-1
7969	13473	-1-(-23-(4+56))-(-789A-B)	B-(A9+8*(-765-432)+1)
796A	13474	-1*(-23-4-56-789A-B)	-B-A*(-987-6-5)-(432+1)
796B	13475	1-(-23-4-56-789A)+B	B*(A98-7+(65-4)*-32)*-1
7970	13476	1-2-3*-456*7+89+A*-B	B+A+9+8+7*6*5*4^3-2^1
7971	13477	-1*-2*-3*(4-5*(-6+7*8)*9)-(A-B)	-B-A+9+8-(-7654-321)
7972	13478	123-4-56-(-789A-B)	B+A+9-8+(7-6*5*4-3)^2*1
7973	13479	123-(45-6-789A+B)	-B+A-(9-8-(7654+321))
7974	13480	-1-2+3+4+5+6+7+89A+B	B+A+9+8+7*6*5*4^3+2^1
7975	13481	-1-2-3+5+6-7+89A*B	B-A-9+8+7654+321
7976	13482	1-(2-34-56-789A)+B	B-(A+98-7)+6*5*(-4+321)
7977	13483	-12+3*(456+7)-89*A*-B	-BA-(9-8765-43*-21)
7978	13484	-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+89)*AB	B-A9*-87+6*(5+43-21)
7979	13485	-1-(234-56)-(-7+89*-AB)	B+A-9-8+7654+321
797A	13486	123-(-4+56-789A)+B	B*(A9+8-(-765-4))-(-3+2+1)
797B	13487	1-(234-(56-7))-89*-AB	B+A+9+(8-7-6*5*4+3)^2+1
7980	13488	1-((-2^3-4^5)*(6+7)-8*9)+A-B	-B+A+9*-8*(-76+5)+4321
7981	13489	123-45-6+789A+B	-B-A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3-2^1
7982	13490	1234-(-5-6-7)+8*9AB	-B-(A-98*76-5*432)+1
7983	13491	12-3+4+5+6+7-89)*-AB	-B-A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3^(2-1)
7984	13492	123-456-7-89A*-B	B+A+9+8+7*(6*5*4^3+2)^1
7985	13493	-1-2+3*(45-6)+789A-B	-B+A*(-98-7)*(-6-5)-(43-21)
7986	13494	-12+3*45-(6-789A)-B	BA-98-7-65*(-4-3)*21
7987	13495	1-(2+3)-(-4+5-(-6+7+89A)*B)	B+A+9+8+(-7+6*5*4+3)^2+1
7988	13496	-123-4-5-6+7+89*AB	-BA9+8765+4*-3*-21
7989	13497	12-(-34-(56+789A))+B	-B+A+9+8+7654+321
798A	13498	-1+234-(567-89A*B)	B+A+(-9*(-8+7*-6)*-5+4)*-3*2+1
798B	13499	-1+2-3*-456*7+8-(-9-A)-B	B-(A-9)+8-(-7654-321)
7990	13500	1-2-(3-(-4+56*-7))-89A*-B	B+A*-9+876*5+4321
7991	13501	123-(45-6)-(-789A-B)	B+A-9+8-(-7654-321)
7992	13502	1+2*3+4+5+6+7+89A-B	B+A+9-8*(7+(-6-5-4)^3)*2^1-1
7993	13503	-1-(-2+3^4(4-(5-6)))*)-7*8+9+A-B	B+A+9-(8-7654-321)
7994	13504	-123+4-5-(67-89*AB)	-B-A9*-87-6*(5-4)*-32*1
7995	13505	-12-3+4+5+6+7+89*AB	-B-A-9*8+7*6^5/4-3^2-1
7996	13506	123-456+7-89A*-B	-B-A+9*8+(7-6*5*4-3)^2-1
7997	13507	-123-4-56-7+89*AB	BA-98+7654+321
7998	13508	-1*(-2-3+4+5+6+7-89A)*B	-B+A*987-654+321
7999	13509	-123-4-(-5-6)*(789+AB)	-B+A-(98*76-5*-432*-1)
799A	13510	12*(34+567-(-89-(A+B)))	B+A+9-8*((7-(6+5+4)^3)/2-1)
799B	13511	123-4-(5+6-789A)+B	B+A-9+(8+7+6+5+4)^3/2-1
79A0	13512	1-(234-5-67)+89*AB	B+A-9*-876+543*(2+1)
79A1	13513	-12-(345-6*7)-89A*-B	-BA-(-9-8*7)-6*5*(4-321)
79A2	13514	-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+89)*A*B	B+A9*87-6*(-54+3+21)
79A3	13515	-123-(-4+56+7+89*-AB)	B+A-9*8+7*(6^5/4-3^2)^1
79A4	13516	(-1-2^3*4*5)*(-6+7+8*9)-(A-B)	B-A9+8765+43*-21
79A5	13517	1+2+3-(-4-5-6)*(-7+89+AB)	-B-A*-987-(6-5+4+321)
79A6	13518	1-2-3+4+5-6+7+89A-B	B+A+9*8-7*(-6*-5/-4^1-3+2)-1
79A7	13519	123+4-5-6+7+89A-B	B+A+9-(-8-(7654+321))
79A8	13520	1+2-3*4+5-(6+7+89*-AB)	BA9+87+65*4*32*1
79A9	13521	1234+5+6+7+89A-B	BA9-(-87-65*-4*-32-1)
79AA	13522	1234-5-6-7-89*A*-B	B-A-9*8*7+(-6-5)^4*3*-21
79AB	13523	123-4-(5-6)-(-789A+B)	BA+9-87-65*(-4-3)*21
79B0	13524	-123+45*6+7+89A+B	B+A+(-9+8-7*6*5)/-4^1-3-2+1
79B1	13525	1-2*(-3+4+5)-(-6-7+89)*-AB	B+A+(-9+8-7*6*5)/-4^1-3^1(2-1)
79B2	13526	1-(-23+4*56)+7+89*AB	BA-98+76*(-5-4+3)*-21
79B3	13527	1*23*(456+7-8-9-AB)	B+A+(-9+8-7*6*5)*-4^3+2*1
79B4	13528	-1-23*-4+5+6+7+89A-B	B+A-9-8+7*6*(5*4^3+2)^1
79B5	13529	123+4-(-5+6-789A)-B	-B-A*-987-6*(-5+4)*3*-21
79B6	13530	12345-6-7+89*A-B	B*A*(98-7+6-5-4*3+21)
79B7	13531	1234-(5-6789)-(-A+B)	B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3-2^1
79B8	13532	1234-5+6+7+89*(-A+B)	-B-(A-9*8-7654-321)
79B9	13533	12-(3-456)-78*(-9-AB)	B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3^(2-1)
79BA	13534	1-2-34-5*6+7+89A*B	B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3+2-1
79BB	13535	-12-34*-5-6+7+89A-B	B+A+9*8+7*6*5*4^3+2^1
7A00	13536	1*2*3*(-4+5+6)*(-78-9-AB)	B+A-98*-76-5*(-432-1)
7A01	13537	1-2+3+4*(-5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B	-B+A*987+6+5+4-321
7A02	13538	-1-23*(-4+5)*-6+7+89A+B	B+A-9*8-7*(-6^5/4+3)+2^1
7A03	13539	-1-(2+3*-4+5-(6+7+89A))+B	-B+A-9*-8-7-65*(4+3)*-21
7A04	13540	-12+3*-456*-7+8*-9*(A-B)	-B+A9*87+(6+5)*(-4-(-3-21))
7A05	13541	1234+5+6+7+89A-B	BA+9+87*(65+43+2)*1
7A06	13542	12345+6-(789*A+B)	-B-A9*8-7+6*-54*-32*1
7A07	13543	1234-(-5-6789-(-A+B))	BA98-7*(654-3*-21)
7A08	13544	-123-45+6+7-89*-AB	B-A9+876*(-5+3*21)
7A09	13545	123-4-(5-(6+7+89A+B))	B+A+(-9+8)*-7*-6*(-5*4^3-2^1)
7A0A	13546	1234-(5-67-8*9AB)	B+A+9-8+7*6*(5*4^3+2)^1
7A0B	13547	1-2+34-(56*7-89A*B)	B-A-(98-76)*(-54-321)
7A10	13548	1-2+34*5-6-(-789A+B)	B+A+9*8+(7-6*5*4-3)^2-1
7A11	13549	(-1-(2^1(3+4)-5^6))^7/8-9+A-B	-B-A-9+876*5+4321
7A12	13550	-1+23*4+5+6+7+89A+B	-B-A9*-87-6-5*-43+21
7A13	13551	123+4+5-6+7+89A+B	B-A*(-9-876-54-32-1)
7A14	13552	12345-(6+7+89*A-B)	B*(-A98+7-654*-3-2-1)
7A15	13553	123+4-5+6+7+89A+B	B+A-9*8+7*6^5/4-3-2+1
7A16	13554	1-23-4*-567-8*-9A*B	-B-A-9-8*(-765-432+1)
7A17	13555	123-4+5-(-6-7+89A)+B	B+A-9*8+7*6^5/4-3+2-1
7A18	13556	1234+5-(-67-8*9AB)	-B-A-987-6*-54*(32+1)
7A19	13557	-1-234-5-6+7+89A*B	B+A-9*8+7*6^5/4+3-2-1
7A1A	13558	-123+45-(-67+89*-AB)	B+A-9*8+7*6^5/4+3-2^1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7A1B	13559	$1-234-5-(67-89A^*B)$	$BA-9^*8^*(-7-65)+4321$
7A20	13560	$123+4-5^*-6+789A-B$	$B+A+9-8-7^*(-6^5/4+3^2+1)$
7A21	13561	$-1-2-345+67-89A^*-B$	$-BA+9-(-8+76)^*(54^*-3+21)$
7A22	13562	$123+4^*5-6+789A+B$	$-B-A-(9-8^*(765+432))^*1$
7A23	13563	$123+4+5-(-6-789A-B)$	$B^*(A-9-(-876+5-(-4-(3-2))))^*1$
7A24	13564	$12345+6+789^*-A+B$	$B-A^*-9+(8+7)^*654-321$
7A25	13565	$-1+2-345+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*6^5/4+3^2-1$
7A26	13566	$12^*(34+567-(-8-(-9+AB)))$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*6^5/4+3^2^1$
7A27	13567	$-1-(234-5)-(67-89A^*B)$	$-B-A+9+876^*5+4321$
7A28	13568	$-1-2^*(-3+4+56^*-78)+9AB$	$B-A9^*-87-65^*-4+32^*-1$
7A29	13569	$-1+2-3-45+(-6+7-89)^*-AB$	$-B+A-9-876^*-5+4321$
7A2A	13570	$1-234-(56+7)-89A^*-B$	$B-(A+9-(87-65^*(4+3)^*-21))$
7A2B	13571	$-1-2+3-4^*-5^*-6^*(-7-89)+AB$	$-BA-9^*-87^*-6+543^*21$
7A30	13572	$-123-(4-5+6)-(7-89^*AB)$	$B+A98-7+65^*4^*(32+1)$
7A31	13573	$123+45-6+789A-B$	$-B-A9^*(-87-6)+5^*-4-321$
7A32	13574	$-123-4-5+6-7+89^*AB$	$B+A^*9-8+7654+321$
7A33	13575	$-1+2-(-3+4-5^*-67)+89A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(8+7)+(6^*-5^*4+3)^2^*1$
7A34	13576	$(-1-(2-3^*(4-5+6)^*7))^*8-9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+98+7654+321$
7A35	13577	$1+2-3^*(45+67)-89A^*-B$	$-BA+9876-5^*(432+1)$
7A36	13578	$12-345-(-67+89A^*-B)$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*(6^5/4+3)/(2-1)$
7A37	13579	$1-23+4^*56^*-7^*-8+9^*-AB$	$-B-A+9-(8^*(-765-432)+1)$
7A38	13580	$-12^*-345^*(6-(7+8)^*9+AB)$	$B+A-9-8/-7^*(6^5+4^4(-3^*-2^*1))$
7A39	13581	$1+(-2-3-4^*(-5+6^*-7)^*-8)^*-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(5^*432+1)$
7A3A	13582	$-1-(2-34-5^*6^*-7-89^*AB)$	$-BA+9876+5^*432^*-1$
7A3B	13583	$(-1^*-2/-3-4^*(5+6^*7))^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5^*432+1$
7A40	13584	$1-234-56-(-7+89A^*-B)$	$-B+A9^*(87+6)-5-4-321$
7A41	13585	$123+45+6+789A-B$	$-B^*(-A-98-765+4-(3+21))$
7A42	13586	$-1-2-(3+45-(-67+8))^*(-9A+B)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+(6+5+4)^3/2)^1$
7A43	13587	$1-2+34^*56+78^*(9+A^*B)$	$-B-(-A-9)-(-876^*5-4321)$
7A44	13588	$-1+2+3^*4+5^*-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9-8+7^*(6^5/4-3^*2)^1$
7A45	13589	$-1+2+3^*456^*7+89-(A-B)$	$B-A+9-876^*-5+4321$
7A46	13590	$-1234-5^*-67+89AB$	$B+A^*9+8+7654+321$
7A47	13591	$12-(3+4^*-567-8^*9A^*B)$	$-B-(-A9+8-(7654+321))$
7A48	13592	$1+2-34+5-(6-7+89)^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*8+7^*(6^5/4+3+2)^1$
7A49	13593	$-123-(-4+5^*6^*7)-89A^*-B$	$B+A-98^*(-76-(54-32)-1)$
7A4A	13594	$1^*-2^*(-3-4)^*(-5-(6-789+AB))$	$-BA9+8-76^*5^*(4-32)-1$
7A4B	13595	$123+45-6+789A+B$	$-B+A^*987+65-4-321$
7A50	13596	$123+4+5+6+789A-B$	$-B-(-A-98-7654)+321$
7A51	13597	$-1-234+56^*(78+9-A^*-B)$	$B-A+(-98-76)^*(-54-3+2-1)$
7A52	13598	$-1-(-2+3^*45)-(6-7-89^*AB)$	$B-A-(-98-7654)+321$
7A53	13599	$1-234-56^*(-78-9-A^*B)$	$BA+98^*(76-(-54+32))^+1$
7A54	13600	$1234-5-(-6+7)-89^*A^*-B$	$-B-A9^*-87+6^*(5+43+2^*-1)$
7A55	13601	$-1+2^*-34-56-7+89^*AB$	$-B+A-(-9-8^*(765+432)-1)$
7A56	13602	$1+2345^*6+7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^5/4-3^2-1$
7A57	13603	$-123-45-(-6-7+89A)^*-B$	$BA9+8+(76-54)^*321$
7A58	13604	$-1-2+3^*(4+5-6)^*7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9-(-8765+43^*21)$
7A59	13605	$-123+4^*(-56+7-89)^*(-A-B)$	$B-A^*(-987-6)+5-4-321$
7A5A	13606	$-12-3-45-67+89^*AB$	$BA-9-8+7654+321$
7A5B	13607	$123+45+6+789A+B$	$-B+A9-(-8-(7654+321))$
7A60	13608	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4+56-7-89^*(-A-B))$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^5/4-3-2+1$
7A61	13609	$-1-234^*5+6-7+89AB$	$-B+A^*(9-8)^*(76-543)^*2^*-1$
7A62	13610	$-123-45+67+89^*AB$	$B-(A-9^*876)-(-54^*-32+1)$
7A63	13611	$1-234^*5+6-7+89AB$	$BA98+7^*-654-321$
7A64	13612	$-12+3-45-67-89^*-AB$	$B-A-9^*-876-54^*-32+1$
7A65	13613	$-1-(2+3+45^*-67)-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A9-(8-7654)+321$
7A66	13614	$-1^*2^*(3+4-(5+6^*789)-AB)$	$B-A^*-987+6+54-321$
7A67	13615	$-1+2^*(3456+789-AB)$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^5/4+3/(2-1)$
7A68	13616	$-1-(-234+56-789A)-B$	$BA9-87^*6^*-5^*4-321$
7A69	13617	$-12-34-5-67+89^*AB$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^5/4+3+2^*1$
7A6A	13618	$1+234-56+789A-B$	$B-(-A-98-7654)+321$
7A6B	13619	$1-2-(3-(-45-67-89^*-AB))$	$B+A-9-8+7^*6^5/4+3^*2+1$
7A70	13620	$-1^*(2-3-(4^*56+789A-B))$	$B+A+9-8+7^*6^5/4-3^2-1$
7A71	13621	$-1-(-2+3)-(-45+67-89^*AB)$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^5/4-3^*2-1$
7A72	13622	$1+234-56^*7-89^*-AB$	$BA-9+8+7654+321$
7A73	13623	$-1-234-5-(6+7)-89A^*-B$	$-BA-9-(-8^*-7+6^*-5^*(4+321))$
7A74	13624	$-12-3+4^*56+789A+B$	$BA+9-8+7654+321$
7A75	13625	$-123+4+5^*6-(-7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A^*987-(-65-4+321)$
7A76	13626	$1-(-2-3^*(4+5-6)^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B-A-9+8765+43^*-21$
7A77	13627	$-1+2^*-34-5+6^*-7+89^*AB$	$B+A-9+8+7^*6^5/4-3+2^*1$
7A78	13628	$1^*2-(-3+45+67)-89^*-AB$	$B+A^*(9-87)^*(6+5^*-4)+321$
7A79	13629	$1+2+3-45-(67-89^*AB)$	$B+A9+8+7654+321$
7A7A	13630	$-12+3-4^*-56+789A+B$	$B+A+9^*876-54^*-32-1$
7A7B	13631	$-12+3^*-456^*-7-8^*(-9-A)+B$	$B+A^*-9+(87-65+4)^*321$
7A80	13632	$-1+2-34-5-67+89^*AB$	$-BA^*(-98-(-7+6+5+4-3-21))$
7A81	13633	$-1-234+5-6-7+89A^*B$	$-B+A^*-9^*8+7^*6^*(5-4)^*-32^*1$
7A82	13634	$12+3^*-4^*-5^*(6+78-(-9A-B))$	$-B-A^*-987-6^*54+32+1$
7A83	13635	$-1-234-(5-6+7-89A^*B)$	$B+A+9-8+7^*6^5/4+3+2^*1$
7A84	13636	$1^*-234-5+6-7+89A^*B$	$-B-A9^*-87-6^*5^*-4^*-3^*(-2+1)$
7A85	13637	$-123+45^*(-6+7)-89^*-AB$	$B-A^*9^*(8+7)-6^*54^*(-32-1)$
7A86	13638	$-1+234-56+789A+B$	$B+A+9-8+7^*6^5/4+3^2-1$
7A87	13639	$-1^*(-234-(-56+789A+B))$	$-BA-98^*7-6^*54^*-32+1$
7A88	13640	$1+234-56+789A+B$	$BA+9+8+7654+321$
7A89	13641	$1-2-34-56-7-89^*-AB$	$B+A^*(987-(65-4)-(-32+1))$
7A8A	13642	$1234-5+6789-A^*-B$	$-BA-(-9+87+6^*-543^*(2+1))$
7A8B	13643	$1-2+3+4^*56-(-789A-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^5/4-3/(2-1)$
7A90	13644	$1+2-34+5-67+89^*AB$	$B-A+9+8765-43^*21$
7A91	13645	$1-(-2+34+56+7+89^*-AB)$	$BA98-76^*-5-4321$
7A92	13646	$-1-234+5^*(-6+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A-(9-8765)-43^*21$
7A93	13647	$1-234+5+6-7-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^5/4+3-2^*1$
7A94	13648	$1+2+3+45^*-6^*-7+8^*9AB$	$-B-A+9^*8+7^*6^*5^*(-4+321)$
7A95	13649	$-1-23-4+5-67-89^*-AB$	$-BA9+8765-4+321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7A96	13650	$1*23-(45-(67+89*AB))$	$-B-A-9+8*76*(-5*4+32+1)$
7A97	13651	$1+23-45-67-89*-AB$	$BA+9-(8+7)*(-65+4+3+21)$
7A98	13652	$1234+5+6789-A*-B$	$BA+98*76+5*-432*-1$
7A99	13653	$-123-4+56+7+89*AB$	$-B+A9*87+6*(54+3)-21$
7A9A	13654	$-12-3-4*-5*-67+89AB$	$B+A+9+8+7*6^5/4+3^2-1$
7A9B	13655	$1-2-34-56+7+89*AB$	$B+A+9+8+7*6^5/4+3^2^1$
7AA0	13656	$1+2*34-5*67+89A*B$	$B+A-9*(8+7)*(-65+4-3-21)$
7AA1	13657	$-1-23+4+5-67-89*-AB$	$-BA+98765+4+321$
7AA2	13658	$-1*2*(-3456-789-A*-B)$	$-B+A*9-876*-5+4321$
7AA3	13659	$-1*(23-(4-56)-(-7+89*AB))$	$-B-A+9*-8*(765+43*-21)$
7AA4	13660	$-12-(3+4-5)-67+89*AB$	$-B+A9*87-65+4+321$
7AA5	13661	$-123-(4-56-7-89*AB)$	$B-A*(98-76+5+4)*(-32-1)$
7AA6	13662	$-12+3+45*6+789A-B$	$-B+A*9+87*7*(65+4)*3-21$
7AA7	13663	$1234-(5-6789)+AB$	$-B+A9*87-6-5+4+321$
7AA8	13664	$-1-23-4-56+7+89*AB$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6*5*4-3)^2+1$
7AA9	13665	$-1-2-3-4*5*67+89AB$	$B+A+9-8+7*(6^5/4+3+2)^1$
7AAA	13666	$-12-(-3-(-4+5)+67)+89*AB$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6^5/4-3-2)^1$
7AAB	13667	$-123-(45+67-89A*B)$	$B+A-9*8-(7-6-5*4)^3*2^1$
7AB0	13668	$123+4*-5*-6+789A+B$	$B-A*(-987-6)+54-321$
7AB1	13669	$1+23-4*-56+789A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7)*-6*-5*(-4-3)-2/1$
7AB2	13670	$12-34-56+7-89*-AB$	$-B+A-9-8*76*(5+4-(3+21))$
7AB3	13671	$-1-(-234+5)-(6-(789A-B))$	$-BA9-8*(-76-5-4*321)$
7AB4	13672	$-123+4-(-5-67)+89*AB$	$B+A+9-8+7*(6^5/4+3*2)^1$
7AB5	13673	$1+234-(5+6-789A+B)$	$B*(A+98+765+4+3+21)$
7AB6	13674	$-12-(-3-4-5+67)-89*-AB$	$B-A9*-87-65-4+321$
7AB7	13675	$-1-2-34+5+6*-7+89*AB$	$-B+A9*87+6-5+4+321$
7AB8	13676	$1+234-5*6+789A+B$	$B+A-9-8-7*(-6^5/4-3^2)+1$
7AB9	13677	$1-2-(34-5*-6)-7+89*AB$	$-B-A98*-7-6*(-5-4-321)$
7ABA	13678	$-12-(3+45*-6)-(-789A-B)$	$B+A-9*-8-7*(-6^5/4+3)-2/1$
7ABB	13679	$-1-2-3+4+5-67+89*AB$	$-B-A*-9-8*(-765-432-1)$
7B00	13680	$-1*2*3*-4*5*(6-7)*(8-(-9+AB))$	$B+A+9+8-7*(-6^5/4-(3+2))-1$
7B01	13681	$-1+234+5-(6-789A+B)$	$B+A+9+8+7*(6^5/4+3+2)^1$
7B02	13682	$-1*(-234-5+6-789A+B)$	$-BA+9*-8*(-76-5+4+32*-1)$
7B03	13683	$123+4-56*7+89A*B$	$B+A-9*(8-7*((6/(5-4))^3+2^1))$
7B04	13684	$-12-3-(45-6)-(7-89*AB)$	$-B*(-A+9-876-5+4+3-2-1)$
7B05	13685	$1+234-5+6-(789A+B)$	$B+A98*7-654*-3+2*-1$
7B06	13686	$1-23+4-5+6*-7-89*-AB$	$B+A-9-8-7*(-6*5*4+3)^2*1$
7B07	13687	$-1-23-45+6+7+89*AB$	$B+A*987-65*4+3*-2*1$
7B08	13688	$1-23-4+5+6*-7+89*AB$	$-B-A9*-87+6*5+4+3+21$
7B09	13689	$12-3-4-56-(7+89*-AB)$	$B+A98*7-(-654*3+2*-1)$
7B0A	13690	$12+3-45*-6+789A-B$	$-B+A*987-(-6-5)+4*-3*21$
7B0B	13691	$1-(2-3)-(45+6)-(7+89*-AB)$	$-B-(A9-8)-7-6*-5*(4+321)$
7B10	13692	$1-2+3*4+5-67-89*-AB$	$B-A*(-987+65)+4+321$
7B11	13693	$-1+234-(5-6)-(-789A+B)$	$-B-A*-987-6+5*-43-21$
7B12	13694	$-1*-234-(5+6-789A)+B$	$B+A+9*8+7*6^5/4-3*2-1$
7B13	13695	$1+234+5+6+789A-B$	$BA+9*8+7654+321$
7B14	13696	$1-2-(3-4)-56+7+89*AB$	$-B+A9+87-65*(-4-3)*21$
7B15	13697	$-1+23+4*5*-67+89AB$	$-B+A9-876*-5+4321$
7B16	13698	$12+3*4*5*(-6-(-7+89))*AB$	$BA+98-7*6*54*(-3-2*1)$
7B17	13699	$1+23-4*-5*-67+89AB$	$-B-A*(-987+65+(43-2)*-1)$
7B18	13700	$-1-234+56-7+89A*B$	$B-A*-9+87*(-6-5)*4*-3-(-2-1)$
7B19	13701	$-1-23+45-67+89*AB$	$B+A+9*8+7*6^5/4+3-2-1$
7B1A	13702	$-1*(2+3*-45*(67+8)-(-9A-B))$	$-B-A+9876+5*-432-1$
7B1B	13703	$1-23+45-(67-89*AB)$	$-B-A+9876+5*-432*1$
7B20	13704	$-1+23-4-(56+7+89*-AB)$	$-BA9*(8-7-(6-54)+32-1)$
7B21	13705	$-1+234-(5-6-789A-B)$	$-B+A*-9*-8+7654-3-21$
7B22	13706	$-1*(-234+5-(6+789A)-B)$	$B*(A+9+876-5-4-3-2-1)$
7B23	13707	$1-2-34+(5-6)*7-89*-AB$	$-BA9-8+7*(6-54)*-32*1$
7B24	13708	$-1+2-34-(-5+6+7-89*AB)$	$-BA9-8+7*(-6+54)*32+1$
7B25	13709	$1-(-2-3)-(45+6)+7-89*-AB$	$-B+A9-8*(-765-432)-1$
7B26	13710	$12-3-4*56-7+89A*B$	$-B+A9+8*(765+432)*1$
7B27	13711	$12-34-(5+6+7+89*-AB)$	$-B+A*-9*-8+7654+3-21$
7B28	13712	$-1-2345*-6+7*(8-9AB)$	$BA-9+876*5+4321$
7B29	13713	$12+3-4*-5-(67-89*AB)$	$-B-A*-9+8765+43*-21$
7B2A	13714	$-1-234+56+7-89A*-B$	$B+A-9+(8+(7-6*5+4)^3)*-2*1$
7B2B	13715	$-1+234+5+6+789A+B$	$B-(-A9+8+7*6*5*(4-321))$
7B30	13716	$-1*-23*-4*(-5+6-(7-8)-9A-B)$	$-B-A*-98+7654-321$
7B31	13717	$-1+23*45+(6-789-A)*-B$	$BA-9-8*(-765-432+1)$
7B32	13718	$12-(-3+45-6+7-89*AB)$	$-B+A9+8*(765-(-432-1))$
7B33	13719	$-1-2-(-345-6)-(-78+9)*-AB$	$B+A9-876*-5+4321$
7B34	13720	$1+23-4-(56-7+89*-AB)$	$B-(A-9876-5*(-432-1))$
7B35	13721	$1-2+34-56-7+89*AB$	$B+A-9-8-(7-6-5*4)^3*2-1$
7B36	13722	$-1-(-2+34-(5-6)-7)-89*-AB$	$-B+A+9876-5*432-1$
7B37	13723	$1-(-23-45*6-789A-B)$	$-B+A+9876+5*432*-1$
7B38	13724	$1-(-2-(34+5)-(-67-89*-AB))$	$B-A+9876+5*-432-1$
7B39	13725	$12+34-5-67+89*AB$	$B-A-(-9876-5*432*-1)$
7B3A	13726	$-12-3-4+5-6-7-89*-AB$	$B-A+9876+5*-432+1$
7B3B	13727	$-1+23-45+6-(7-89*AB)$	$B-A*-987+6-5*43-21$
7B40	13728	$1+23-(-4+56-7+89*-AB)$	$B*(A-9)*(876+5+(-4+3)*-2-1)$
7B41	13729	$12+3*4*5*6+789A-B$	$B+A-9-(8+7-6*5-4)^3*2-1$
7B42	13730	$-123-(-4+56+7)-89A*-B$	$BA+9+876*5+4321$
7B43	13731	$1-(2-3-45)-67-89*-AB$	$B+A-9-(8+7-6*5-4)^3*2+1$
7B44	13732	$12-(-3+45)+6-(-7-89*AB)$	$B+A9+8*(765+432)*1$
7B45	13733	$-1+2-(-3-45)-(67+89*-AB)$	$-B-A98-76*-5*(-4+32)*1$
7B46	13734	$12-34+5*-6*7+89A*B$	$BA98-7*-65-4321$
7B47	13735	$1+2+3+4+5-67-89*-AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+(-6*5*4+3)^2+1$
7B48	13736	$-12+3-(4+5)-(-6-7-89*AB)$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6^5/4+3+2)^1$
7B49	13737	$-12-3*4-(5-6)-(7+89*AB)$	$-BA9-87*6*(-5+4+32+1)$
7B4A	13738	$-12+3*(4-5)-(-6+7)*-89*AB$	$B-A*-98+7654-321$
7B4B	13739	$-12+3456-(-7+8*9*A*-B)$	$BA+98+7654+321$
7B50	13740	$12-3+45-67+89*AB$	$B+A9-8*(-765-432-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
7B51	13741	-12+345*6+78*9A-B	-BA+9+(-8-7)*(-654+3)-2+1
7B52	13742	123-4+5*-67-89A*-B	-BA-9+8+7-6*543*(-2-1)
7B53	13743	1-2+3-(-4+5)-(-6+7)-89*-AB	BA+9+8*(765+432)*1
7B54	13744	-12+3-4+5+6-7-89*-AB	BA+9-8*(-765-432)+1
7B55	13745	-123-45+6-7+89A*B	B+A+9876-5*-432*-1
7B56	13746	12+3+45-67-89*-AB	B+A+9876+5*-432+1
7B57	13747	-123-(45+6)+7-89A*-B	-B-A9*-87-6+5*4+321
7B58	13748	-1-(-234-56)+789A-B	B+A+9-(8+7-6*5-4)^3*2*1
7B59	13749	-12-3+45-6*7-89*-AB	B+A+9-(8+7-6*5-4)^3*2+1
7B5A	13750	12+34-56-(-7+89*-AB)	B+A*-9*-8+7654-3-2*1
7B5B	13751	1-2-(3+4-5-6+7+89*-AB)	BA+9-8*(-765-432-1)
7B60	13752	-1-2+345*6+78*9A-B	-B+A9+8765-43*21
7B61	13753	12-(3456+7-8*-9*-A*B)	B+A-9*(-8-7*6*5)*(4+3)-2/1
7B62	13754	-1+2*(3456+7+89*A)-B	B-(A98-76*-5*(4-32))-1
7B63	13755	-1+23+45-67-89*-AB	B+A+9+8-(7-6-5*4)^3*2-1
7B64	13756	-1*(-23-45-(-67-89*-AB))	B+A+9+8-(7-6-5*4)^3*2*1
7B65	13757	-1-2-3-(-4-5)+6-7+89*AB	B+A+9+8-(7-6-5*4)^3*2+1
7B66	13758	12-3-4-5-6-(-7-89*AB)	B-A9*-87-6+5*(-4-321)
7B67	13759	1-(-2+3-(-4-(5-6)-(-7-89*AB)))	-B-A9*-87+6+5*4+321
7B68	13760	-1-23-(4+5+6*-7+89*-AB)	-BA+9-(-8-7-6*-543*(-2-1))
7B69	13761	12+3-45+6*7+89*AB	B-A9+8-(7+6*543*(-2-1))
7B6A	13762	1-23-4-5-6*-7+89*AB	-B*-A+9+8+7*6^5/4+3^(2+1)
7B6B	13763	-12+34-5-6-7-89*-AB	-B+A*9876+6*(-54+3+21)
7B70	13764	-12-3-(45-67)+89*AB	BA9+87*(6-5-4)*(-32-1)
7B71	13765	12+3-4*5+6+7+89*AB	-BA98-(7+654*(-32+1))
7B72	13766	-123+4-(-5+6*7-89A*B)	B+A-9*(8-7)*6*5*4*3-21
7B73	13767	-1-2*(-3456-789)-A*B	B-A*-987+(6*-5*4+3)*-2*-1
7B74	13768	1-2-34*5+6-7-89A*-B	B+A+(9*-8-7)*-6*(5-4*-3*2)+1
7B75	13769	1-(23-45)-(6+7)+89*AB	B+A9*87+654-321
7B76	13770	-1+23+45+6+789A+B	B+A-9*-8*((-7*-6+5)*4+3)-2+1
7B77	13771	-1*(-234-56-789A-B)	B+A*(987+6+5+4-32*1)
7B78	13772	1+234-(-56-(789A+B))	B*(A+98+765+4+32-1)
7B79	13773	-12-34-(56+(-7+89A)*-B)	B+A+9*8*(7*6+5+(4*3)^2)^1
7B7A	13774	-12+34*(-5+6)-7+89*AB	B-(A9-8765-43*-21)
7B7B	13775	-12+34-5+6-7+89*AB	B+A+9+8*7+(6*5*4-3)^2/1
7B80	13776	-1*(-2-(-34+567-89))*(A+B)	B+A+9+8*7+(6*5*4-3)^2+1
7B81	13777	-123-4-(5+6)-(7-89A*B)	-B-A+9-8-7*(-6^5/4-3^(2+1))
7B82	13778	-12-3+45-6-7+89*AB	B+A+(-9+8-7*6)*-5*4^3-(2+1)
7B83	13779	-1+2-(3+45-(67-89*-AB))	BA-9+8*7-6*5*(4-321)
7B84	13780	-12+3*456-78*(-9A-B)	-B+A9*87-6+5*43*2*1
7B85	13781	-123+45+6-(7-89A)*B	BA98-7-65*4*(-3+21)
7B86	13782	-1*(-23-4-(-5-6+7)+89*-AB)	B+A+(-9+8-7*6)*-5*4^3+2-1
7B87	13783	1-23+45-6+7+89*AB	B*(A+987-6*(54-32)*1)
7B88	13784	-12+3+45-6-(7-89*AB)	B+A*987-6+5*(-4-32)-1
7B89	13785	-123-(-4-(-5-6))-(-7-89A*-B))	BA+9+8765-43*21
7B8A	13786	-1-2-34-5+6+7+89*AB	-B-A-9-8+(7-6+5*4+3)^(2+1)
7B8B	13787	1+2+3-45+6+7+89*AB	B-A-9+((-8-7)*-6+5)*((-4*-3)^2+1)
7B90	13788	-1+2-(-34-5)-(-6+7-89*AB)	B-(A+9-8*(76+543)*2*1)
7B91	13789	1-23*4+5-(67-89A*B)	B+A+9*8+7+(-6*5*4+3)^2/1
7B92	13790	-1+2+34-5+6-7-89*-AB	B+A+9*8+7+(-6*5*4+3)^2+1
7B93	13791	-123-(4+5-(-6+7))+89A*B	B+A*(9+876)-5-43*-21
7B94	13792	1+23+4+5+(-6+7)*89*AB	B+A+(-9+8*7)*(6*(5-4*3)^2-1)
7B95	13793	-12-3-4+56-7+89*AB	B+A*-9*-8+7654+32*1
7B96	13794	123-45-(67-89*AB)	-B*(-A+9-876+54+3*-21)
7B97	13795	-123+4+5-6-7-89A*-B	BA98+7-65*-4*(3-21)
7B98	13796	-1-23-4+56+7-89*-AB	B+A-9*-8*7*(-6*5-4/-3*2)-1
7B99	13797	1-2-3*45-6-7+89A*B	B+A+9*8*7*(6*5-4/3*2)^1
7B9A	13798	-123+4+5*6*7+89*AB	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/(4+3/2-1))
7B9B	13799	-123-(4-(5+6))-(-7+89A*-B)	-B-A+(9+8*7)^(-6+5+4)-3-2+1
7BA0	13800	-1+2-(34-5)-(-67-89*AB)	B+A-9*(8-7*(-6-5)*-4*(3+2)+1)
7BA1	13801	-1-2+3*4-5-6*-7-89*-AB	B+A*(9+876)+5-43*-21
7BA2	13802	1+23-4+5*6-7+89*AB	BA98+7*(-654-32*1)
7BA3	13803	-12+34*-5-(-6-78-9)*AB	BA98-7*(654+32)+1
7BA4	13804	1+2+3*(-4+567)+8*9AB	-B-A+(9+8-7-6+5*4)^3+2-1
7BA5	13805	1+23+4+5+6+7-89*-AB	B*(A9-876-54*(-32+1))
7BA6	13806	12-3+45-6-7+89*AB	-B+A9*87-(-65+4-321)
7BA7	13807	-1+23-45+67-89*-AB	-BA+9+(8-76)*-5*(4-32)*-1
7BA8	13808	-123+4+5*(-6+7)+89A*B	B+A-9*(8-7*(-6-5)*-4*(3+2))-1
7BA9	13809	1+23-45+6+7+89*AB	-BA9+8765+432-1
7BAA	13810	-12-(-3-45-6)-(-7+89*-AB)	-BA9+8765+432*1
7BAB	13811	-123+4-5-(-6-7-89A*B)	-BA9+8765-(-432-1)
7BB0	13812	1-2+3+4+5-(-6-7+89*-AB)	-B+A9*87-(65-(432-1))
7BB1	13813	1+2+3*-45+6-7-89A*-B	-B-A+9+(8-7+6+5)^4/3^2+1
7BB2	13814	1+2-3+4*-5-(-67-89*AB)	B+A+(-9+8-7*6*5)*(4^3+2)-1
7BB3	13815	-1-23+4+5+6+7+89*AB	B-A9-(-87-6*-5*(-4-321))
7BB4	13816	-1+2-3-4-5+(-6-7+89A)*B	-B*(-A-9-876+5-(-4+3)-2+1)
7BB5	13817	-123-(45+6*(-7-89A)*B)	-B-A+(9+8)*(-7*6*5+4^(3+2))^1
7BB6	13818	-1+23*-45-(-6+7-89AB)	B+A+(9+8*7)^(6+5+4)-3^(2+1)
7BB7	13819	-1+234*5+(6+8)*(9+AB)	B+A+9-8-7*(-6^5/4-3^(2+1))
7BB8	13820	-12+345-(6-789A+B)	B+A-9-8*((7+6-5+4)^3-2)*-1
7BB9	13821	-12-(-3-4)+56+7+89*AB	B+A+(-9+8*-7*6)*-5*(4+3+2-1)
7BBA	13822	-12+3+4-5+6+7+89*AB	BA-9*(-8+7+65)*-4*(-3-2)*-1
7BBB	13823	12+3+4+5-(-6*7+89*-AB)	B+A+(-9/-8+7*6)*-5*-4^3+2^1
8000	13824	-12-(-3+4-5-(67+89*AB))	B+A+(-9/-8+7*6)*-5*-4^3+2+1
8001	13825	-123-45+67-89A*-B	B-A-9*-8*(76+54+32)*1
8002	13826	-123+456+789A-B	BA-9+87-6*-5*(-4+321)
8003	13827	12+34-(-5-6-7)+89*AB	B*(A-9+876-5*-4+3*2*-1)
8004	13828	1+2-3-4-(5+6)*-7+89*AB	B+A9*87+65-4+321
8005	13829	1-(2+3-4)-(5-67-89*AB)	-B-A*-987+6-(5-4*-32-1)
8006	13830	1+2+3-4+56+7+89*AB	B+A+9+8*((7+6-(5-4))^3-2-1)
8007	13831	-1-(2-345)-(-6-789A+B)	-B-A*-987+(6-5)*4*(-32+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8008	13832	$1 - (-2+3-4-56) - (-7+89^* - AB)$	$B+A+(-9/-8^*-7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8009	13833	$-1+2-(-34+5^*-6-7)-89^*-AB$	$B-A^*-987-6^*(-5-4+32-1)$
800A	13834	$1-2-3-45-67-89A^*-B$	$B-A9^*-87-65+432-1$
800B	13835	$-1+234-(56^*7+89A^*-B)$	$-B-A^*(-987+6)-(5+4)+3^*-21$
8010	13836	$-1-(-23+4)-(-56+7+89^*-AB)$	$B-A^*(98-7+6)^*(-5-4-3)+21$
8011	13837	$1+2+345-6+789A-B$	$B+A-9+(8-7+6+5)^{\wedge}4/3^*2+1$
8012	13838	$1+2+3^*45-67+89^*AB$	$B-A^*(-987+6+5)-(43+2)^*1$
8013	13839	$1-2^*(-345+6)+78^*(9+AB)$	$B+A^*987+6^*(-54+32-1)$
8014	13840	$1-2+3^*4-(5-67-89^*AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*6^*(5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8015	13841	$1+2-(-3+4)+5+67-89^*-AB$	$BA-(-98+7)-6^*-5^*(-4+321)$
8016	13842	$-12-(-345-(-6+789A+B))$	$B-A+9-8^*7^*(-6+5^*43-2^*1)$
8017	13843	$-1-2+345+6+789A-B$	$B-(-A+9-(8-7))+6^*5^*(4+321)$
8018	13844	$1^*-2+345+6+789A-B$	$BA+9+87+6^*-5^*(4-321)$
8019	13845	$1-2+345+6+789A-B$	$B+A+9^*(8+7-6-5)^{\wedge}4^*3^*2/1$
801A	13846	$12-3-4+5+67-89^*-AB$	$B+A+(9+8-7-6+5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2-1$
801B	13847	$-1+2+345+6+789A-B$	$-B+A^*987+6-(-5+43)^*(2+1)$
8020	13848	$-123+456+789A+B$	$-B+A^*987-65-(43+2+1)$
8021	13849	$12-3-(45+67)-89A^*-B$	$B^*(A+98-(-765-(43-2)+1))$
8022	13850	$-1-2-(-3-45)-6^*-7+89^*AB$	$B+A9-(87-65+4)^*-321$
8023	13851	$-1-2+34+56-7+89^*AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6-5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
8024	13852	$1^*-2-(-34-56)-(7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6-5+4)^{\wedge}3-2/1$
8025	13853	$-1-2+345-(6-(789A+B))$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6+5)^{\wedge}4/3^*2-1$
8026	13854	$-12+345+6+789A+B$	$-B-A-(9+87+65-4)^*-3^*21$
8027	13855	$1-2-34+5-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9^*-87^*6+543^*21$
8028	13856	$1-(23+4+5-(-67-89A^*-B))$	$-B-A^*(-987-6+54)+321$
8029	13857	$-1+2-(-345+6)-(-789A-B)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6-5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1$
802A	13858	$-1-(2+3^*-4-56^*(78+9A)+B)$	$-B-A^*-987-6^*-5^*-4-(3-2)^*1$
802B	13859	$1+23+4-56-(-7+89A)^*-B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(-7^*6^*5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))^{\wedge}1$
8030	13860	$12+3+4+5+6+7+89^*AB$	$B^*(-A98+765+43)^*(-2-1)$
8031	13861	$1+23+4-5+6+7+89^*AB$	$BA+9876-5^*(432+1)$
8032	13862	$-12+34^*5-67+89^*AB$	$-B+A987-6-54^*3^*21$
8033	13863	$123-(4+56)-(-7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^*2)+1$
8034	13864	$-1-23-4-(-5+6+7+89A^*-B)$	$B+A-9-(8-7^*-6^*-5^*(4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}1))$
8035	13865	$1^*-23-4+5-67-89A^*-B$	$BA+9876+5^*-432-1$
8036	13866	$1-23-4+5-67+89A^*B$	$BA+9876-5^*-432^*-1$
8037	13867	$1-2-(-345-6-789A)+B$	$BA+9876-5^*432+1$
8038	13868	$1234-56-78^*(-9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8-7^*6)^*(-5/4^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
8039	13869	$-1-(-2-345)-(-6-(789A+B))$	$-B-(-A+9)-((8+7-6)^*-543^*2-1)$
803A	13870	$12-(-345-(-6+789A)-B)$	$-BA-98^*-7^*6-5^*4^*-321$
803B	13871	$1+2-(-34-56)+7-89^*-AB$	$-B^*(A9-87^*6-543-2+1)$
8040	13872	$12-3-4-(-5-6^*(-78-9A)^*-B)$	$-B+A^*987-6-(54+32)+1$
8041	13873	$-12-3+4-5-(67+89A^*-B)$	$-B+A-9+(8+7)^*654-32+1$
8042	13874	$123-45-6+7+89^*AB$	$-B+A987+6+54^*-3^*21$
8043	13875	$-1-23^*-45+(-6-(-78-9))^*AB$	$B-A^*-987-65-43+2^*1$
8044	13876	$-12-3-4-56-7-89A^*-B$	$B+A^*987-65-(43-2-1)$
8045	13877	$-1+2+34^*5-67+89^*AB$	$-B-A+(-9-8^*(7+6))^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^*2)-1$
8046	13878	$12-3^*(4+5)-67+89A^*B$	$-B+A^*987-65+4-3-21$
8047	13879	$12-34-5^*(6+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A+(9-8^*7+6)^*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
8048	13880	$-1+2-3-(4-(-5-67+89A^*B))$	$-BA+9^*(8-76)^*(-5-4^*3-2^*1)$
8049	13881	$1-23-4-56+7-89A^*-B$	$B+A^*987+6^*-5^*-4^*(-3+2)^*1$
804A	13882	$12+34-(-56-7-89^*AB)$	$B+A^*-9^*-87-(6^*-543+21)$
804B	13883	$123+4-5-6^*7-89^*-AB$	$-B-A^*-987+6-54-32^*1$
8050	13884	$-1-(2+3+4+5+6)-(-7+89A)^*-B$	$-B-A^*-987-(65-(4+3-21))$
8051	13885	$12-34-56-(-7-89A^*B)$	$-B-A-9-8+(7-(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8052	13886	$-1^*2^*(34^*-5-6^*-7+89)^*AB$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*(6+(5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2^*1)$
8053	13887	$-123-(-4-5-67+89A^*-B)$	$-B-A^*-9^*87+6^*543+2^*1$
8054	13888	$-123-45+6^*(-7-89)^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A9^*87-(6-5-432+1)$
8055	13889	$1^*-23-45-(-6+7+89A^*-B)$	$B-A^*-987-65-(-4-(-32-1))$
8056	13890	$-1+2^*345^*(6+7)+89A+B$	$B+A^*987-65+4-32^*1$
8057	13891	$-12-3-(-4^*-5-6^*-7)+89A^*B$	$B+A-9-(-8^*7-6^{\wedge}5^*(-4/-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
8058	13892	$-1^*(-2-3-45-67+89^*-AB)$	$-B+A987+6^*(-543-21)$
8059	13893	$1^*(-2+3)^*-4-56-7+89A^*B$	$-B+A^*(98-7)^*6-5+4321$
805A	13894	$-1-2-3+4-(-5+67)+89A^*B$	$B+A+(-9+8-7)^*6/(5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
805B	13895	$-1-2-(3-4)-(56+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A^*(987-6)-5-4-32+1$
8060	13896	$-12-(-3+4)-(56-(7+89A^*B))$	$B+A987+6-54^*3^*-21$
8061	13897	$-1-(-2-3)-4-(56+7)-89A^*-B$	$-B-A-9-(-8^*(7+6^*(5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
8062	13898	$1+2-(-34+5+6^*(78+9A)^*-B)$	$B-A^*-987-(65+43-21)$
8063	13899	$12+3-4-5-67+89A^*B$	$-B+A^*987-65-4+3+2^*-1$
8064	13900	$123+45-67-89^*-AB$	$B-A^*-987-65-(-4+3+21)$
8065	13901	$1-23^*-4+5^*6+7+89^*AB$	$-B-A-9+8+(7-(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8066	13902	$1^*-2^*(3-4)^*(5+6+789-AB)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7+6-5+(-4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
8067	13903	$1-(-23+45-6^*-7)-89A^*-B$	$-B-A+(9+8+7+6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
8068	13904	$12-(-3-45-67)-89^*-AB$	$-B^*(-A-9-(8+765-4^*32^*-1))$
8069	13905	$-12+3-45+6-7-89A^*-B$	$-B-A^*-987+6-54+32^*-1$
806A	13906	$1+2^*(-3+4-5+67)+89^*AB$	$B+A^*987-65-(-4-3+21)$
806B	13907	$12-34+5-(6^*7+89A^*-B)$	$-B-A^*-987-6-(54-(-3+2)+1)$
8070	13908	$-1+23-4-5-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(7-6^*(5-4^*3^{\wedge}2))+1$
8071	13909	$12-(-3+4-5-(-67+89A^*B))$	$B-A^*(-987-(-6-5)-4)-(-3+21)$
8072	13910	$12+3-4-(56+7+89A^*-B)$	$-B+A^*9^*87+6^*543+21$
8073	13911	$-1-2+3+4^*5-67+89A^*B$	$BA-98+7+6^*543^*(2+1)$
8074	13912	$-12+34-5-67+89A^*B$	$B+A9^*87+6-(5-432+1)$
8075	13913	$1234-5-6+78^*(9A+B)$	$-B-A+9+(8-7+6^*5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8076	13914	$123-4+5-(6+7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A987-6^*(543+21)$
8077	13915	$1-(-23-45-67)+89^*AB$	$B+A^*987+6-54-3-21$
8078	13916	$12^*(-3+4+5-(-6-789+AB))$	$-BA^*(9-8-76-5-(4-3)-(2+1))$
8079	13917	$-1^*(23-45+67+89A^*-B)$	$-B+A9^*87+6^*(5+43^*2)-1$
807A	13918	$1-23+45-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(7+6-5^*-4/3^{\wedge}2)+1$
807B	13919	$12-3+4+5+6+(-7+89A)^*B$	$B+A-98-7^*-65^*(43-21)$
8080	13920	$1^*2^*(3456+789+A+B)$	$-B+A^*987-(65-(-4-3+21))$
8081	13921	$1-2^*(-3456-(789A)-B)$	$-B+A9+87^*(6+54-3)^*2+1$
8082	13922	$123+4+5-6-7-89^*-AB$	$BA-98^*7-6^*54^*-32^*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8083	13923	-1-2+34-5-67-89A*-B	-B+A*987-6+5*(4+3*2)*-1
8084	13924	12+3-4-56+7-89A*-B	B-A*-987+65*(-4+3)*(2-1)
8085	13925	1-2-34-5-6+7+89A*B	-B-A*-987+6-(54-3-(2-1))
8086	13926	123-(4-5)-(-6+7+89*-AB)	B+A*987+65-4*-32*-1
8087	13927	-1+23+4-56-7+89A*B	B+A-9-8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2-1
8088	13928	1*(2-3)*-4*(5*678-9A*B)	-B+A*987-(6-5+43-(2-1))
8089	13929	1-(-23-4+56)-7+89A*B	B+A-9-8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
808A	13930	-12*(3+4-(5-(6-789)))-A*-B)	-B-A*-987*(6-5)-43+2*1
808B	13931	-123+45+67+89A*B	B+A*987-6-54-(3-2-1)
8090	13932	12+3+4-56+7+89A*B	B+A*9*87+6*543+21
8091	13933	1-2*(-34-(56+7))+89A*B	-B+A9*(87+6)-5+4*(-3-21)
8092	13934	123+4+5+6-7-89*-AB	-B-A*(9-8+7)-(6+5)*43*-21
8093	13935	12+3-45-6+7+89A*B	B+A-9+(8-7+6*5*4-3)^2-1
8094	13936	123+4-(5+6)-(-7-89*AB)	B+A-9+(8-7+6*5*4-3)^2/1
8095	13937	-1-2*3+45-67-89A*-B	B*(-A+987+6*5-4*-32*-1)
8096	13938	-1+2+34-56-7-89A*-B	B-A*-987-6+5*-4-32+1
8097	13939	12-34-5-(6-7)*89A*B	-B+A*(9+8-(7-654-321))
8098	13940	12+34-5-(67+89A*-B)	-B-A98*7+6*5*43*-2-1
8099	13941	-12-3-4-(5-(6-7)+89A*-B)	B+A-9-8*(-7-6*(-5*4+3)^2)+1
809A	13942	-1-23-(4-5-6)-(-7+89A*-B)	B-A*(-987-(6+5)+4)+3*(-2-1)
809B	13943	1+23+4-56+7-89A*-B	B+A9*(8-7)*-6*(-5*4-(3+2-1))
80A0	13944	-12*3*4*(5-(6+78))-(-9+A-B))	-BA-9*-8+7*-65*(-43+21)
80A1	13945	-12+3+4-5-(6+7-89A*B)	B+A*987+6-54+3-(2-1)
80A2	13946	12-(3+4-5*-6)-7-89A*-B	-BA-(9+8)-765*(4*3-21)
80A3	13947	-12+3-4+5-6-7+89A*B	B+A+9-8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
80A4	13948	-1-(-2-(3+45-67-89A*-B))	B*(A-(9-876-(54-32))-1)
80A5	13949	-123-4+56*(78-9+AB)	B-A*-987*(6-5)-43-(2-1)
80A6	13950	1+2+3+45-67-89A*-B	B-A*-987-6+5-43*(-2+1)
80A7	13951	1+2-34+5+6+7-89A*-B	B-A*(9-8+7+6+54*(3-21))
80A8	13952	-1-23+4-5-(6-7-89A*)*B	-B+A+9+8*(-7+6+5-4*-321)
80A9	13953	-12-3+4-5-(6-7)-89A*-B	-B+A*987-65+43*(2-1)
80AA	13954	-1-2-3-4-5+6-7-89A*-B	B-A+98+7-6*5*(-4-321)
80AB	13955	1-(-2+3*45*(-67-8))-(-9+A*-B)	-B+A*987+65+43*-2+1
80B0	13956	(-1*-2+(-3-4*-5*6)*7)*(8+9)+A-B	B-A*-987-6*5*4-3*-21
80B1	13957	-12-(-3-4+5)-(-6+7+89A*-B)	B+A+9-(-8*(7+6*(5+4*3)^2)+1)
80B2	13958	-12+3+4-5-(6-7)*89A*B	B+A+9+8*(7+6*(5*4-3)^2)^1
80B3	13959	-12-(-3+4-5-6+7-89A*B)	B-A*987*(-6+5)-(-4-32)*-1
80B4	13960	1-2+3-4+5-6-7+89A*B	-B+A*987+6-54-(32-1)
80B5	13961	1-2+3-45-6*-7-89A*-B	-B+A-(987+654)*(-3-(2+1))
80B6	13962	-1+2*3-(-456-78)*(9+A)+B	B+A+9+8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2/1
80B7	13963	-1-(23+4*-5)-(6-7)-89A*-B	B+A+9+8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
80B8	13964	-1-2-(3+4-(5+6))-(-7+89A*-B)	-B+A*987+6+5-43+21
80B9	13965	12+34-56+7-89A*-B	B+A-9+(-8-7*6*5)*-4^3+2-1
80BA	13966	123+45-(6+7)-89*-AB	BA-9*-8*(76-(5-4)-3)*2*1
80BB	13967	123+4-5+6*7-89*-AB	-B+A9*87+65-432*-1
8100	13968	-1-(23+45)+67-89A*-B	-B-A9*-87+65+432+1
8101	13969	-1-23-(-456-(789A-B))	B+A*987-6-54-32*-1
8102	13970	-1-(-23-45+67)+89A*B	-B*-A*(-9+8)*(-76+5-(4+32))*1
8103	13971	-12+3+4-5+6+7-89A*-B	B-A*-987-6*(5-4)*(3-2*-1)
8104	13972	1-2-3*-45*(67+8)-(-9-AB)	B+A+(-9*-8+7+6*5)*4^3+2-1
8105	13973	-12-3+4*-5*(6-7)+89A*B	B+A+(-9*-8+7+6*5)*-4^3*-2/1
8106	13974	-12-3*-4+5-6+7-89A*-B	B-A*-987-65+43-2+1
8107	13975	12-3-45+(6+78+9)*AB	B-A*-987-(-6*(5-4+3)-2)*-1
8108	13976	-1-2-(3-4)-5+6-(7-89A*B)	-B-A+9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
8109	13977	-1+23+4*-5-(6-7+89A*-B)	B+A*987-(6-5-4-(32-1))
810A	13978	-12-(-34-(5-6-7))+89A*B	-B-A*-987-65+43+21
810B	13979	123-45*(6-7)+89*AB	-BA+9+8*7*(6-5*(-43+2)+1)
8110	13980	-1+2*(34-(56-7))+89*AB	-B+A*987+65-43-21
8111	13981	-12+3-4*5-6*-7+89A*B	-B*(A-9)*(-876-5+4-3-21)
8112	13982	-1+23+4-5-(6+7-89A*B)	B+A+9-(-8+7*-6*5)*4^3/(2-1)
8113	13983	1*(2-3)*(4-5)*6+7+89A*B	-BA-98*7*6-(5432+1)
8114	13984	1-23-(-45+6)-(7-89A*B)	B+A+9+(-8-7*-6*5)*-4^3+2^1
8115	13985	-12+3-45+67-89A*-B	-BA-98*7*-6-(-5432-1)
8116	13986	-12+3+456+789A-B	B+A*(987-6)-5+43-2+1
8117	13987	1+23-45+6*7-89A*-B	-B-A+9+8*7*(6-5+4)^3*2-1
8118	13988	-12+3+4+5-6-7+89A*B	-BA+98-7*65*(-43+21)
8119	13989	123-(-4-56)-(7-89*AB)	B+A+9*(8*7*6*5-4^3*2)^1
811A	13990	-12+34-(5-(6-7))-89A*-B	B+A9*87+65+432+1
811B	13991	-1-2-3+456+789A-B	B+A*-987*(-6+5)-(4+3+2+1)
8120	13992	123+45+6+7-89*-AB	B*(A-(98+7-654)+321)
8121	13993	1-23-(-456-789A)+B	BA98+7*-654+3*-21
8122	13994	-1234+567+89AB	-B-A*-987-6-5+43-21
8123	13995	-1+2-3-(-456-789A)-B	B-A*-987-(-6+5+4)*(3-2+1)
8124	13996	1+23+4-5+6-7-89A*-B	BA-9-8-7+6*-543*(-2-1)
8125	13997	-1-23-4+56-7+89A*B	B+A*987-(6-5)*4-3+2+1
8126	13998	-1+234-5-67+89*AB	B-A-9-8-7*65*(-43+21)
8127	13999	1-2-(-3-456-789A+B)	-B-A*-987+6*-5+43-(2-1)
8128	14000	1+23-4-(-5+6-7-89A*B)	B+A-9*8*-7-65*(-4-3)*21
8129	14001	-1+2+3+456+789A-B	B+A*987-654*(3-2-1)
812A	14002	-1*(-2-3-(456+789A-B))	-B+A*987+65-43-2-1
812B	14003	1-(-2-(3+456))+789A-B	-BA+9+(8+76-5)*-4*32*-1
8130	14004	-12+34-5+6+7-89A*-B	B+A+(9*-8-7)*-6*(-5+4^3)*2^1-1
8131	14005	-1-(-2-34)-(5-(6-7))+89A*B	B+A+(9*-8-7)*-6*(-5+4^3)/2+1
8132	14006	12+34-5-(6+7+89A*-B)	-B-A9*-8+7654-32-1
8133	14007	-1*(2-3-456-7-(8+9))*(A+B)	-B+A98*7-6*(-54-321)
8134	14008	-12+3+456+789A+B	B+A*987+6+5-4-3-(2-1)
8135	14009	123-45-67-89A*-B	B+A*987-6*-5-(4-3-(2-1))
8136	14010	12-3*45*-67+8+9AB	B+A-9/(8+7)*((-6^5+4)*3+2-1)
8137	14011	-12+3+45+6-7-89A*-B	-B+A*987+6+(-54+32)*-1
8138	14012	-1+2*-3+456-(-789A-B)	-B-A9*(-87-6)-(-5+4+32+1)
8139	14013	-1-2-3+456+789A+B	B-A*-987-6*(-5+4+3)*(-2+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
813A	14014	$12+3+456+789A-B$	$B*(A9-8-(-7-6+543))*2*-1$
813B	14015	$1-2-3+456+789A+B$	$-B-A-98*(-7+65+43)*(-2+1)$
8140	14016	$1-2+34*(-5+6)+7+89A*B$	$B+A*987-6-(5-43)-21$
8141	14017	$1+2-(34-5-67)+89A*B$	$-B+A9*8+7654-3-21$
8142	14018	$1-2-3*-45+6*(78+9A)*B$	$B+A*987+6-54-3*-21$
8143	14019	$-12-(3-45-6)-(-7+89A*-B)$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*-6-5^4)*3-(2+1)$
8144	14020	$12+34-5-(6-7)+89A*B$	$-B+A*(987-6)-(-54-32)-1$
8145	14021	$12-3+45-6-7-89A*-B$	$B-A*(-9-876)-5*4*-3*21$
8146	14022	$-1-2*3-4*5+67+89A*B$	$B-(-A-98-7+6*-543*(2+1))$
8147	14023	$-1+23+456+789A-B$	$-B-A9*-8-(-7654-3)-21$
8148	14024	$1+23-45+67-89A*-B$	$B+A*987-(-65+43+2+1)$
8149	14025	$1+23+456+789A-B$	$B*(A-(9+8-(-76-5)-43))*-21$
814A	14026	$1-2*-3+456+789A+B$	$B+A+9/(8+7)*(6^5+4)*3+2-1$
814B	14027	$-1*(2-345*6-789*A+B)$	$-B-A*-9-(-8-7)*654-(-3-21)$
8150	14028	$-1+2-(-3-45)-(-6-7+89A*-B)$	$B-A9*-8-(-7654-(-32-1))$
8151	14029	$-12+3-(4+5-67-89A*B)$	$B-A9*-8+7654-32*1$
8152	14030	$-12+34*5*-6-7+89AB$	$BA98+7*-654-32*1$
8153	14031	$1+2*(-3+45*-6)-(-7+89)*-AB$	$B+A*987-6+54-3-21$
8154	14032	$12-3+4*(5+6)+7+89A*B$	$B+A-(-9*(-8*(-7*-6-5^4)/3+2)-1)$
8155	14033	$-12-3-4+5+67+89A*B$	$BA98+7*(-654-3-2*1)$
8156	14034	$1*-2-(-3-4)-(-56-(-7-89A*-B))$	$BA9+87*-6*5*-4-(32+1)$
8157	14035	$12-3+45-6+7-89A*-B$	$B+A*987+6-5-4+32-1$
8158	14036	$12-(-3-456-789A)+B$	$-B*(A+9-876-5-43+2+1)$
8159	14037	$-1+2-(-3-4)+56-(7-89A*B)$	$B-A*-987+65-4-32+1$
815A	14038	$1*23-(-4+5-6*7)+89A*B$	$-B+A9*87-(6-(543-2))-1$
815B	14039	$12+3+45+6-7-89A*-B$	$B+A9*8-(-7654+3+21)$
8160	14040	$1+2-(3+4+5-67-89A*B)$	$-B-A-98*(7-65-43)+21$
8161	14041	$1-(2-(3-4))+56+7+89A*B$	$B-A-9*(-8-7+6-543)*2*1$
8162	14042	$12*(34-5+678-9A+B)$	$-B+A*987+6+54-3*2-1$
8163	14043	$1-2-34*5*6-7+89AB$	$-B+A*987-6-(-54-3*-2*-1)$
8164	14044	$1-2-(3-4)-(-5+67-89A*-B))$	$B-A*987*(-6+5)+4+32+1$
8165	14045	$-1-(-23-456-789A)+B$	$BA98-7*(654+3)+2*-1$
8166	14046	$123-45+6*-7+89A*B$	$-BA9+87*(65+43+21)$
8167	14047	$12+3-456+(7+89)*AB$	$B+A*987-6*5+43+21$
8168	14048	$-1*2*-3-(45*-6+7*89*A-B))$	$-B+A*987-(6+54-3+2)*-1$
8169	14049	$1-(2-3)-(-4-56-7-89A*B)$	$BA9+8*(7-6)*543*-2*-1$
816A	14050	$12+3-(-4-56-(-7-89A*-B))$	$-B+A*(987+6)-(-54+3*-21)$
816B	14051	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7-89A*-B$	$B-(-A987+654*(3+2)-1)$
8170	14052	$-1-(-23-4*56)+7+89*AB$	$B+A-(-9-8)+7*65*(43-21)$
8171	14053	$123-4-5-67+89A*B$	$B+A987+6*(-543-2)+1$
8172	14054	$1-2-(3-4-(5+67))+89A*B$	$-B+A987-6*(-543+2)*-1$
8173	14055	$-12+34-(-56-(-7-89A*-B))$	$-B-A+9*((-8-7)/-6^5+4+3/2)^1$
8174	14056	$-12+3*-4*-5*-6*-7+89*-A*-B$	$BA-9*(-8-(765-4)-321)$
8175	14057	$12+3-4-5+67+89A*B$	$B+A*-9*-87-6*(-543-21)$
8176	14058	$12-34*-5*-6-7+89AB$	$-B+A*987+65*(4-3)+2*1$
8177	14059	$-1+2+34*5*-6+7+89AB$	$BA98-7*654+3*(-2-1)$
8178	14060	$-1+2*-3+4*-5*6*7*-8+9AB$	$BA98+7*(-654-3+2)-1$
8179	14061	$1+23-(-4-(56-7)-89A*B)$	$B-(-A987-6*-543-(-2-1))$
817A	14062	$-1-(-23-(45+6+7)+89A*-B)$	$BA98-7*654-3*2*1$
817B	14063	$-12-3+45*6+7-89*-AB$	$B-A*(-9-876)-543*-2*1$
8180	14064	$1*2*(3456-78-9A*-B)$	$BA98-7*654-3-2+1$
8181	14065	$12-(-3-4+5-(67+89A*B))$	$BA98+7*-654-3*(-2-1)$
8182	14066	$1-(2+34)-5+6*(-7-89)*(-A-B)$	$B-A*-987-6-5+43+21$
8183	14067	$-1*-23*(456-7+8-(-9+AB))$	$BA98-7*654+(3-2)*-1$
8184	14068	$1+23-(-4+5-67-89A*B)$	$BA98+7*-654-(-3+2)-1$
8185	14069	$1-2*3*4*(5-67)*8-(9+AB)$	$BA98-7*654*(3-2)+1$
8186	14070	$-12+34-5+67+89A*B$	$BA98-7*654+3-2+1$
8187	14071	$123+4+5-(67-89A*B)$	$B+A9*(87+6)-(-5+4+3-2+1)$
8188	14072	$123+4-(56+7)+89A*B$	$B-A9*-87+6+543-2-1$
8189	14073	$-1-(-23-4-56-7)+89A*B$	$BA98-7*654+3*2-1$
818A	14074	$-1-(-23-4)-(-5-67)-89A*-B$	$BA98-7*654+3*-2*-1$
818B	14075	$1*-23+45-(-67+89A*-B)$	$-B-A9*(-87-6)-(-54+32+1)$
8190	14076	$-1-(-23-(-4+5+67)+89A*-B)$	$B+A987+6*(-543+2*1)$
8191	14077	$-1*(-234-(-5+6-7-89*-AB))$	$B+A*987+65-4+3*(2-1)$
8192	14078	$1-(-23-(4+5-6))-(-7+89A)*-B$	$-B-A+(-9-(8+7-6+5))*(-432+1)$
8193	14079	$123-(-4-5-6+(-7-89A)*B)$	$B-A*-987-6*(5-(-4-3+21))$
8194	14080	$1-(-234+5)-(-6-7-89*AB)$	$B*-A*(98-76+54+32)*-1$
8195	14081	$-1-2+34-(-5-67-89A*B)$	$-B-A*(-987-6-5)-(-4+3+2-1)$
8196	14082	$1-(-2-34-56-7-89A*B)$	$B-A9*(-87-6)-(-5-(-4+3)-2*-1)$
8197	14083	$1-2+34-5-(-67-89A*B)$	$B+A9+8*-76*-5*4-321$
8198	14084	$123+45-6*(78+9A)*-B$	$B+A+(9*-8+7-6^5/4)*(-3*2-1)$
8199	14085	$(-1-2*3)*-4*(5-(6-7*8^9))-(-A-B)$	$B-A*-987+(-6+5*4)*3*2*1$
819A	14086	$-1*(-23+45-6*(-7-89))*(-A-B))$	$B+A+9-8*(7-(6*5+4*3)^2)^1$
819B	14087	$-1+234+5-(-6+7)*-89*AB$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(6+5*(4+3)^2)+1$
81A0	14088	$1*2-(-34-5)-(-6-(7+89A)*B)$	$-B-A*-987+6+54+32+1$
81A1	14089	$-1-(23-4-56+(-7+89A)*-B)$	$B+A987-6*543+21$
81A2	14090	$-1+234-5+6+7-89*-AB$	$BA98-7*654-(-3-21)$
81A3	14091	$1+234-(5-6)*7-89*-AB$	$B*(-A+9)*(-876-5+4-32)*1$
81A4	14092	$-1+23-45*-6-7+89*AB$	$-B+A*987+6-5-4*(-3-21)$
81A5	14093	$-1-(-23+4*5*6*7*-8-9AB)$	$BA98+7*65*-4*3-(-2+1)$
81A6	14094	$1-2+3456-78*9*-A-B$	$B+A+(-9-(8-7*-6^5))(-4^3+2)-1$
81A7	14095	$-1-(-2-(34+5)-67)-89A*-B$	$BA98-7*65*4*3-2+1$
81A8	14096	$-1-(-2-3456+78*-9*A+B)$	$BA98-7*-65*4*3*(-2+1)$
81A9	14097	$12+34-(-56-7)-89A*-B$	$B-A*(-987-6)+54-3-21$
81AA	14098	$1-(2+3)-(-45-67-89A*B)$	$B+A+9*(-8+7*6)*(-5*-4+3)*2+1$
81AB	14099	$(1*-2*-3+4)*-5*-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-76-5*-43*-21$
81B0	14100	$-1+2-(-3-45)-(-67+89A*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-(8-7))*(-6-5)*4^3*2-1$
81B1	14101	$123-45+6+7-89A*-B$	$-BA+9*876+5*(432-1)$
81B2	14102	$1+234+5+6+7-89*-AB$	$B*(A9-8+765+43+21)$
81B3	14103	$-1-234-56*-7+89A*B$	$B+A98*7+(65+43)*21$
81B4	14104	$1-(2-3)-(-45-67+89A*-B)$	$-B+A*987-6*5*-4+3*2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
81B5	14105	$1-234 - (-56*7+89A^* - B)$	$BA98+7^* - 654+32-1$
81B6	14106	$1-2^*(3+(4^* - 5+6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7^* - 654+32^*1$
81B7	14107	$-1 - (2+34) - 5^* - 67 - 89^* - AB$	$-BA - 9^* - 876 - 5^* - 432+1$
81B8	14108	$12+34 - (-5 - 67 - 89A^*B)$	$-B+A987 - 6^*5^*4^* - 32^* - 1$
81B9	14109	$12+3456+78^*9^*A - B$	$B+A - 9^*8+(-7^*(6 - (5^*4+3)))^{\wedge}2 - 1$
81BA	14110	$-1+23+(45-6)^*7+89^*AB$	$B+A^*(- 987 - 6 - 5)^*(4 - 3 - 2) - 1$
81BB	14111	$-1 - 2^* - 3^* - 4^*(5 - 6)^*7^*(89 - A - B)$	$-BA - 9^* - 876+5^*(432+1)$
8200	14112	$12^*3^*(4 - 56^* - 7 - 8 - (-9+AB))$	$-B - (-A98 - 7654) - 321$
8201	14113	$12 - (3 - 45) - (-67 - 89A^*B)$	$B^*(A - 9 - 87+654+321)$
8202	14114	$1-2^*(-3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7+8^*9)+A-B$	$BA - 9+87+6^* - 543^*(- 2 - 1)$
8203	14115	$123+45 - 67+89A^*B$	$-B - A^* - 987+6+5^*(43 - 21)$
8204	14116	$1 - 2+3456+78^*9^*A+B$	$-B - A9+8^*(- 76 - (-5 - 4))^*(3 - 21)$
8205	14117	$-1+2 - 3^* - 45 - (6+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A+9^*8^*7^*6^*5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2 - 1)$
8206	14118	$1234 - 5+(-6+789 - A)^*B$	$B+A+9^*8^*7^*6^*5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
8207	14119	$-1+234 - 5 - 6^* - 7 - 89^* - AB$	$-B - A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2 - 1)$
8208	14120	$12 - 3 - 4+56+(-7 - 89A^* - B)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^* - 6^* - 5^*(4+3^*2) - 1$
8209	14121	$1^* - 23^*(4+56^*(- 7+8 - 9) - A+B)$	$B+A9+87+6^* - 543^*(- 2 - 1)$
820A	14122	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)+(-7 - 8)^*9 - (A - B)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^* - 6^* - 5^*(4+3^*2)+1$
820B	14123	$-1 - (234+567 - 89AB)$	$B+A - 9^*8+7^*(- 6 - (5+4))^*3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
8210	14124	$-1^*(234+567 - 89AB)$	$-B+A+98^*7^*6 - (-5432+1)$
8211	14125	$1 - 234 - (567 - 89AB)$	$B+A^*(987+6) - (-54+3) - (-2 - 1)$
8212	14126	$-1+2 - (3 - 4)+56^*(78 - 9+AB)$	$B+A9^*87+6^*(- 5+43)^*(2+1)$
8213	14127	$1 - 2^*3^*(45 - 67) - 89A^* - B$	$B - A+98^* - 7^* - 6+5432^*1$
8214	14128	$-1+23+45+67+89A^*B$	$BA - 9^*(- 8 - 765 - 4 - 321)$
8215	14129	$-12 - 3 - 4 - (5^* - 67 - 89^*AB)$	$-BA9+8+7^*(- 6+54)^*(32+1)$
8216	14130	$1+23+45+67 - 89A^* - B$	$B+A987 - 6^*5^* - 4^*32^* - 1$
8217	14131	$123 - (4+5) - (-6+7 - 89A^*B)$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4 - 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
8218	14132	$(-1 - 2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5+6))^*7 - 8^*9 - (A - B)$	$-B - A^*987+6 - 5+4^*32^*1$
8219	14133	$1234 - 56 - (789 - A)^* - B$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7^*6^*5 - 4^*3 - 2)^{\wedge}1$
821A	14134	$-1 - 2^*(3 - 4567) - 89A - B$	$B - (-A98 - (7654 - 321))$
821B	14135	$-12+3^* - 4^*(- 56 - 789) - (A - B)$	$-B+A+(98 - 7+65)^*(43+21)$
8220	14136	$12 - 3^*4^*5^* - 6+7+89^*AB$	$-B+A^*98 - (7654 - (-32+1))$
8221	14137	$1+(-2^* - 3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6) - 7^*(8+9)+A - B$	$-B - A - 9 - 8+7^*(- 6 - 5 - 4)^*3^{\wedge}2/1$
8222	14138	$1 - 23 - 4 - (5 - (-6 - 7)+89A^*)^* - B$	$B - A98^* - 7+65^*(4+32)+1$
8223	14139	$1+2+3^*4^*56^*(78 - 9+AB)$	$B+A - 9 - (-8^*(- 7^* - 6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2)+1$
8224	14140	$123+4 - 5 - (-6+7)^*89A^* - B$	$B - (-A9 - 8^*(7 - 65)^*(4 - 3)^* - 21)$
8225	14141	$-1+234+56 - 7 - 89^* - AB$	$B - A^* - 9^*(8+76 - (-54+3+2^*1))$
8226	14142	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)+(-7 - 8)^*9+A+B$	$B - A9^* - 8+7654+3^*21$
8227	14143	$1+234+56 - 7 - 89^* - AB$	$BA+98+7+6^*543^*(2+1)$
8228	14144	$((-1 - 2^{\wedge}3)^* - 4+5)^*(- 6^* - 7^*8+9)+A - B$	$-BA - 9+8765+432^* - 1$
8229	14145	$123 - 4 - 5+6 - (-7+89A^* - B)$	$-BA - (9 - 8765) - (432 - 1)$
822A	14146	$1 - 2+3^*4^*56+789A - B$	$-B^*(- A - (9+876+54 - 32 - 1))$
822B	14147	$-12+345 - 67 - 89^* - AB$	$-B - A^*98^*7 - 6543^* - 2^*1$
8230	14148	$-1^* - 23^* - 4^*(- 5 - 6+7 - 8 - 9 - A^*B)$	$B+A+98^*7^*6+5432+1$
8231	14149	$1 - 23^*(- 45+678 - 9AB)$	$-B - A^*(9+87+6)^*(- 5 - 4+3)^*2^* - 1$
8232	14150	$123 - (-4 - 5 - (6 - 7)^* - 89A^*B)$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4 - 3^{\wedge}2+1$
8233	14151	$-1^* - 2^*((-3^* - 4 - 5))^{\wedge}6+7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$-B - A^*98 - (-7654 - 3+21)$
8234	14152	$1 - 23^* - 4+56+7 - 89A^* - B$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4 - 3^*2/1$
8235	14153	$12+3^*(- 4 - 5)^* - 6+7 - 89A^* - B$	$-B - A9^*(- 87 - 6)+54+32+1$
8236	14154	$-12^*(- 34 - 5 - 678 - (9 - A+B))$	$-B - (A9 - 8765+432+1)$
8237	14155	$-1+234+56+7+89^*AB$	$-B - A9+8765 - 432^*1$
8238	14156	$1^*234+56+7+89^*AB$	$-B - A9+8765 - 432+1$
8239	14157	$1^* - 23 - (-4 - 5^*6^*7+89A^* - B)$	$-B - A^*(987+6+5+4)+3+21$
823A	14158	$-1 - 2 - (-345+67) - 89^* - AB$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4 - 3+2+1$
823B	14159	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4 - 5+6)^* - 7^*(8+9)+A - B$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3 - 2^*1$
8240	14160	$1^* - 2^* - 34^*(5+6+7 - 8+9^*A+B)$	$-B - A^*987 - 6^* - 5+4^*32 - 1$
8241	14161	$12 - 3^* - 4^*56+789A - B$	$-BA - (-9 - 8765) - (432+1)$
8242	14162	$-1+2 - (-345+67) - 89^* - AB$	$-BA+9+8765 - 432^*1$
8243	14163	$1 - (2 - 34) - 56^*(- 78 - (-9+AB))$	$-BA+9 - (-8765+432)+1$
8244	14164	$1+2+345 - 67 - 89^* - AB$	$B+A - 9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2/1$
8245	14165	$-12+3 - 4 - 5^* - 6^*7 - 89A^* - B$	$-B+A9^*87+654 - 32 - 1$
8246	14166	$-1+234+5+6+7+89^*AB$	$B+A9+8 - 7 - (6+5)^*43^* - 21$
8247	14167	$123 - (45 - 67 - 89A^*B)$	$B+A^*98+7654 - (3+21)$
8248	14168	$1 - 2 - 3^* - 4^*56 - (-789A - B)$	$B^*(A+9 - 876 - (54+3)+2)^* - 1$
8249	14169	$1+2^*(34+56 - 7) - 89A^* - B$	$B+A+9^*((-8 - 7)/ - 6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)^{\wedge}1$
824A	14170	$-1 - 2^*((-3 - 4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7+8^*9)+A+B$	$-B - A+(-9+8 - 7^*6)^* - 5^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
824B	14171	$12+3+4+5^*6+7 - 89^* - AB$	$B+A+9^*(8^*(- 7 - 6)^* - 5+4)^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
8250	14172	$1+2+34^*5+6 - 7+89A^*B$	$B+A - 9+(8+7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
8251	14173	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/ - 6^*(- 7 - 8)^*9+A - B$	$B - A9^* - 8^*(7+6)+543 - 21$
8252	14174	$12 - 3^* - 4^*(- 56+7)^*(- 8+9 - A - B)$	$-BA - 9+8^* - 76^* - 5^*4+3^*2 - 21$
8253	14175	$12+345 - 67 - 89^* - AB$	$-B - A^* - 987+6 - 54^* - 3+2^* - 1$
8254	14176	$-12+34 - (-5^*67 - 89^*AB)$	$B - (A9 - 8765) - (432+1)$
8255	14177	$1+(-2^* - 3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6) - (7+8^*9)+A - B$	$B - (A9 - 8765 - 432^* - 1)$
8256	14178	$1 - 2 - 34^* - 5^*(6 - 7^* - 8+9) - A - B$	$B - (A9 - 8765+432 - 1)$
8257	14179	$-12 - 345+6+(-7 - 89^*)^* - AB$	$B^*(- A+9)^*(- 876+5 - 43 - (2 - 1))$
8258	14180	$1+2 - 34 - 56^* - 7 - 89^* - AB$	$B+A - 9+8^*(7+(6^*5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
8259	14181	$123+45 - (6+7+89A^* - B)$	$B+A+(9+8+7^*6+5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
825A	14182	$-12^*(- 3+45 - 678 - 9A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8+7^*6+5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
825B	14183	$12 - 3^*4^* - 56 - (-789A - B)$	$B+A+(9+8+7^*6+5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8260	14184	$-1 - 2^*(-3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7) - 8^*9+A - B$	$B+A^*987 - 6^* - 5 - 43^*(- 2 - 1)$
8261	14185	$-1 - 23 - 4+56^*7 - 89^* - AB$	$B - (A+9+8) - (7 - 6^* - 54^*(- 32+1))$
8262	14186	$12+3^*4^*5^*6+7+8^*9^*AB$	$-B^* - A+9^*((-8 - 7)/ - 6^*5^{\wedge}4+3/2)^{\wedge}1$
8263	14187	$-1^* - 2^*(3 - (-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7) - 8^*9 - (A - B)$	$B+A - 9^*(8 - 7^*(- 6^*5+4^{\wedge}(3+2 - 1)))$
8264	14188	$-1 - 2^*(-3456+7 - 89A)+B$	$-B - A - 9^* - 8^*(76+5)+4321$
8265	14189	$1 - 2 - (-34 - 5^*6+7 - 89^*AB)$	$-B^* - A+(-9 - (8 - 7))^*(- 6 - 5)^*4^{\wedge}3^*2 - 1$
8266	14190	$123 - (-456 - 789A - B)$	$B^*A^*(9 - 8+7^*6+54 - (3 - 21))$
8267	14191	$12 - 3^*(4 - 56 - 7)+89A^*B$	$B+A^*98+7654 - 3 - 2+1$
8268	14192	$1 - 2 - 345+6+(-7+89^*)^*AB$	$B - A9^*(- 87 - 6)+5^*(- 4+3+21)$
8269	14193	$123+45 - (-6 - (-7+89A^*B))$	$B - (A9 - 87 - 6^* - 54^*(- 32+1))$
826A	14194	$-1+23 - (45+6)^* - 7+89^*AB$	$-B - A - 9^*(- 8^* - 7^*(- 6^*5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
826B	14195	$123+45 - 6+7+89A^*B$	$-B - A^* - 987 - 6^*(- 54+3+21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8270	14196	$-1*2*(-3456-7+(-89-A)*B)$	$B-A*-98+7654-(-3-2*-1)$
8271	14197	$123-4*-56+7+89*AB$	$B+A+9-8+7*((-6-5-4)*3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
8272	14198	$-123+4-5*-67-89A*-B$	$B+A+9+8*(7+(6*5+4*3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$
8273	14199	$-1+2+345-6*7-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7*-6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$
8274	14200	$1*2*(3-4)*5*(6-(7-8+9AB))$	$-BA*(9+8-7-65+4-32+1)$
8275	14201	$-1+2*-345-(67-89AB)$	$B+A*(987+6+5+4*3-2-1)$
8276	14202	$-1+23-4+5*6*-7-89A*-B$	$-B-A+9+87*-6*(-5-(-4-3)-21)$
8277	14203	$1+2*-345-(67-89AB)$	$-B-A-9*-8*-7*(-6*5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$
8278	14204	$123+4-(-56+7+89A*-B)$	$-B-A9*-87-654*(-3+2*1)$
8279	14205	$-1+2-3-4^{\wedge}5*(-6-7/-8*-9)+A-B$	$B+A+9*8*(7*6*5-4-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
827A	14206	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*-4*(5/-6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$B-A*-987-6-5*(-4-32)+1$
827B	14207	$123+45+6+7-89A*-B$	$-B+A9*87+654-3*(-2+1)$
8280	14208	$1-2345*6-7+8*-9*AB$	$-B-A+(-9+(-8-7)*6*5)*(-4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$
8281	14209	$1-(2+3)-(4-56*7)+89*AB$	$-B-A*(98-(765-4+321))$
8282	14210	$12*(-34-5*(-67+8-9AB))$	$B+A+(-9+8-7*6)*-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
8283	14211	$123-4-(5-67)+89A*B$	$-B+A*98+7654+32*1$
8284	14212	$12+345-6*7-89*-AB$	$-B+A*98-(-7654-(32+1))$
8285	14213	$-1+234-5-67+89A*B$	$-B+A*987-6*(5-4+32)*-1$
8286	14214	$1-(-2*3-4^{\wedge}5*(6-7/-8*9))+A-B$	$-B+A+98+(-76*5)*(432-1)$
8287	14215	$1+234-(5+67+89A*-B)$	$B-A*9-(-8765+432+1)$
8288	14216	$(-1+2*(3-4^{\wedge}5+6))*7/(8-9)+A-B$	$B-A*9+8765-432*1$
8289	14217	$12-3+4*(56-7)-89A*-B$	$B+A+9-(-87+6*-543)*(2+1)$
828A	14218	$123+4+5+6+7-89A*-B$	$B-A9+8*7*(-65-43)*-2*1$
828B	14219	$-123+456-(7+89*-AB)$	$-BA+9876-54*32-1$
8290	14220	$-12+3*(4-(-5-67))-89A*-B$	$B+A9*87-65*4*-3-2*1$
8291	14221	$123-(-4-(5-6-(7+89A)*-B))$	$B-A9*-87+65*4*3-(2-1)$
8292	14222	$12+3*-4*(-5+67)*(-8-9-A+B)$	$BA98-7*(654+3-21)$
8293	14223	$-1-(-234-5+67)+89A*B$	$B-A*-98-(-7654-3)+21$
8294	14224	$1*-2*(3+45)*(-6-7-(-8-9)-AB)$	$-B-A+((-9*-8+7)*-6*-5+4)*3*2+1$
8295	14225	$-1-234+567-89*-AB$	$B-A-(9+87)*(-65-43-(-2+1))$
8296	14226	$1-2+345-6-7+89*AB$	$-B-A+9*8+7*((-6-5-4)*3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
8297	14227	$1-(-2-3-4)-(-56*7-89*AB)$	$-B-A+9*876-5*-432*1$
8298	14228	$1*-2*(-3456-7-89A-B)$	$-B-A+(-9+8)*7-6^{\wedge}5*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
8299	14229	$-1-2-3*4*(56+7-89A+B)$	$-BA+9-8*-76*5*4+32*-1$
829A	14230	$1*2+(-3-4*-5*6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*-8*(76+5)+4321$
829B	14231	$-1+2+3+4*56-(7+89A*-B)$	$B-A*9*-8+76*(5+4-3)*21$
82A0	14232	$-1*-2*(3-((-4^{\wedge}5+6)*7+8))-9+A-B$	$-B+A9*87+654+3+21$
82A1	14233	$-123-(-456-7)-89*-AB$	$B+A*98-(-7654-32)*1$
82A2	14234	$-1*(234-(5+67)+89A)*-B$	$B*(A-9)*(-8-7*6*(-5-43+21))$
82A3	14235	$-12+34*5+67+89A*B$	$-B-A+9*8*(7*6*5-4*3)^{\wedge}(2-1)$
82A4	14236	$1+2*-34*(-5-6)-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7*(-6*5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
82A5	14237	$-123-4*56+(7+89)*AB$	$-B-A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5-4*3)+2/1$
82A6	14238	$1-234+5-(6+7)*8*(-9-AB)$	$-B-A9-8*76*-5*4-(-3+21)$
82A7	14239	$-1*(2-345+6-7-89*AB)$	$-B*-A-9*8*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1$
82A8	14240	$-1*(-23-45)*(67-8+9A-B)$	$-BA+9*8*7+6*543*(2+1)$
82A9	14241	$12+345-(6+7+89*-AB)$	$-B-A9*-87+654+32-1$
82AA	14242	$-1+2+345-6+7+89*AB$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*-6*-5*-4*-3/2+1$
82AB	14243	$-12+34+56*7+89*AB$	$-B+A9*87-(-654-32-1)$
82B0	14244	$1*2*-3*(4+5-678-9AB)$	$B-A+9*876-5*(-432+1)$
82B1	14245	$-1+2345-67+8*-9A*-B$	$-BA+9-8*-76*-5*-4+3-21$
82B2	14246	$1*2*(3456+7-8+9A*B)$	$B+A-9*-8*-7*(-6*5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
82B3	14247	$1+2*-3*-45-6*7-89A*-B$	$-B+A+9*876-5*-432*1$
82B4	14248	$1-2*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6)*7+8-9)+A-B$	$B-A9*8-87+654-3+21$
82B5	14249	$-1*(-2*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7+8*-9+A-B$	$-BA-9+8*76*5*4+3-2-1$
82B6	14250	$-1-2+345+6+7+89*AB$	$-BA-9-8*-76*-5*4*(-3+2)+1$
82B7	14251	$12345-6*7+8*9A*-B$	$B+A*(-9-87-6-543*2)*1$
82B8	14252	$1+234-5+6*-7-89A*-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7*-6*-5*4+3)+2^{\wedge}1$
82B9	14253	$12+345+6-(7+89*-AB)$	$B+A*987+65-(-4-3)*21$
82BA	14254	$-1+2-3+(45-67-89A)*-B$	$-B-A9+8*76*5*4+3*2*-1$
82BB	14255	$12+345-6+7-89*-AB$	$-B+A*987-6*(-5+43)*(-2+1)$
8300	14256	$-1*-23*-4*-56*(7+89+A*B)$	$B*(A-(-98+76))*5(4-3-21)$
8301	14257	$1*2+(-3*-4-5*6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)*7*-6*5*4-(3-(2-1))$
8302	14258	$-1+2*(3+4)*(-567+8)*-9+A+B$	$B+A+9*(8*7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)*2-1$
8303	14259	$1-23*-4-5*-67-89*-AB$	$B+A+9*(8*7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)*2^{\wedge}1$
8304	14260	$1*(-23-4)*5(67-89A+B)$	$-B-A+(9+8)*7*6*5*4+3-2/1$
8305	14261	$1-2*-34+5*6*7-89A*-B$	$-BA+98*-7*6-543*-21$
8306	14262	$1+234-5*6-7-89A*-B$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7)+6)*(-5*-4*(3+2)+1)$
8307	14263	$1+2*(-345-6)-7+89AB$	$BA+9+8*7*6*(54-(-3+21))$
8308	14264	$-12-(3+45*-6)-(-7+89A*-B)$	$-B-A-9+8765-432-1$
8309	14265	$123+45-6+(-7-89A)*-B$	$-B-A-(9-8765)-432*1$
830A	14266	$1-2*(-3-4567-8)+9*-AB$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8765+432-1)$
830B	14267	$12+345+6+7-89*-AB$	$-B*(-A-987+6+5-43*-2-1)$
8310	14268	$(-1+2-3)*(-4^{\wedge}5+6)*7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+7*((-6-5-4)*3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
8311	14269	$1-2*((-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)*7+8)-9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9*876-5*432*1)$
8312	14270	$1*-2*(-3-4+5+6-7+8)*-9AB$	$B+A+(-9+8)*7-6^{\wedge}5*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
8313	14271	$1234-(-567-8*9AB)$	$B+A*987-6*(5-(43-(2-1)))$
8314	14272	$1-2^{\wedge}3-4*-5*-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA9-8-(-7654+321)$
8315	14273	$12+3+(-45+67+89A)*B$	$-B+A*-98*(-7-6)-543-21$
8316	14274	$1-23*(-4-5*6)+789A-B$	$B+A+9*876+5*(432+1)$
8317	14275	$(-1-(-2*3)^{\wedge}4)*5(6+7)/(-7-8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5-4*3)-2^{\wedge}1$
8318	14276	$-1*(2*(-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)*7+8)-9+A-B$	$-B+A*-9*-8*7-6+5432-1$
8319	14277	$-123-4-567+89AB$	$-BA-9-8*-76*-5*-4+3+21$
831A	14278	$1+23*4*-56-(7+8)*-9AB$	$B*(A9-(-8-(765+43)))+21$
831B	14279	$-1-2+345-6*-7-89*-AB$	$BA98-(-76-5*-43*21)$
8320	14280	$-1+2-3*-456+(789A)*B$	$BA98+765-4321$
8321	14281	$1-2+345+6*7-89*-AB$	$-B*-A+9+(-8+7*6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8322	14282	$-1+23*(456-7-89+A-B)$	$-B-A-(-9-(8765-432))-1$
8323	14283	$-1*23*(-456-(-7-89+A-B))$	$-B-A+9-(-8765+432*1)$
8324	14284	$1+23-(45-67-89A)*B$	$-B-A+9-(-8765+432-1)$
8325	14285	$-123+4-567+89AB$	$-B+A*987-6*(5-4*-3)*(-2-1)$
8326	14286	$-1+234+56-(-7+89A)*-B$	$B-(A+9)-(-8765+432+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8327	14287	$-1-2-3^4 5^6-7+89AB$	$-BA-9-8^*-76^*5^4+32^*1$
8328	14288	$1+2^{\wedge}3-4^*-5^*-6^*-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8+7654-321$
8329	14289	$-1+2+3^*-4-5^*(67-89)^*-A^*-B$	$-B-A^*-9^*8^*7+6-5432^*-1$
832A	14290	$-1-2^*((-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7-(8-9)))+A-B$	$BA+98+7+(6+5)^*43^*21$
832B	14291	$(-1/-2+3^*-4+5^*-6^*-7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*-6^*-5^*4-(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
8330	14292	$1^*2^*3^*(4-(5-678-9AB))$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*-6^*-5^*4-3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
8331	14293	$-1+234-5-6+7-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9+((8-(-7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1$
8332	14294	$-12^*(-34-(-5+678+9A)-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*-6^*-5^*4-3^*2-1$
8333	14295	$1+2^*-345+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*-6^*-5^*4-3^*2/1$
8334	14296	$1-2^*((-3-4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7+8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A9^*87-6^*-5^*(4-32)^*-1$
8335	14297	$-1+2^*3^*(-4+5)^*(678+9AB)$	$-BA-9-(-8765-(-4-321))$
8336	14298	$-1^*-2^*3^*(-4+5)^*(678+9AB)$	$-B+A^*-9+8^*-76^*5^*-4^*(3-2)-1$
8337	14299	$-1-2^*(345-6)+7+89AB$	$-B+A^*(987-(6+5)+4-(-32-1))$
8338	14300	$-1^*2^*(34+5^*-6^*7+89)^*-A^*-B$	$-B^*A^*(9-(87-6)-(54+3-21))$
8339	14301	$-1+234-(-5-6+7-89A^*B)$	$B+A+((9+8+7-6-5)^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
833A	14302	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A+9+8765-432-1$
833B	14303	$-1+2^*-3^*(4-5-678-9AB)$	$-B+A+9+8765-432^*1$
8340	14304	$1+234+5-(-6+7)^*89A^*B$	$-B+A-(-9-8765+432-1)$
8341	14305	$1+234+5-6+7+89A^*B$	$-BA-9+8^*(7-6)^*(-54+3^*-21)$
8342	14306	$-1+2^*(34-5^*-6)^*78+9AB$	$B+A-9+8765-432-1$
8343	14307	$1+234-(5-6-7+89A^*-B)$	$B-(-A+9)+8765+432^*-1$
8344	14308	$-12^*(34-5-(678-9)+A^*-B)$	$B+A-(9-8765)-(432-1)$
8345	14309	$(-1+(-2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5+6)+7^*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-(4-3)))/2-1$
8346	14310	$-12+3^*(-4+5^*(678-9))+AB$	$-BA98-7+65^*(-4+321)$
8347	14311	$-12-34+5^*67-89A^*B$	$-B^*(-A-(9-87)-(654+321))$
8348	14312	$((-1+2-3)/-4^{\wedge}5-6)^*7+8+9-(A-B)$	$-BA+9^*(-8+7)^*(65-4)^*(3-21)$
8349	14313	$1+2345-6-7+8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+9+((8^{\wedge}7-6)+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$
834A	14314	$(-1/-2^*-3+4^{\wedge}5)^*(6+7-(8-9))+A-B$	$-B-A+9^*87-6^{\wedge}5^*(4/3-2^{\wedge}1)$
834B	14315	$-1+234+5+6+7+89A^*B$	$-BA-9+8765-4-321$
8350	14316	$-1-2-345^*-6-7-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A9+8765+4-321$
8351	14317	$1-(-234-5-6)+7-89A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7-6^*(5+4-3))^{\wedge}2-1$
8352	14318	$-1-2^*-345-6-(-789A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7-6^*(5+4-3))^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
8353	14319	$-1-2-(34^*5^*(-67+8)-(-9+AB))$	$-B-A^*(-987-6)-(5^*-43-21)$
8354	14320	$-1+2+345+67-89^*-AB$	$-B+A^*987+6^*(54-3)-21$
8355	14321	$1-2^*34^*(-56-7-(89-A+B))$	$B+A+(-9-8-7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}1)$
8356	14322	$1+2+345+67-89^*-AB$	$-B^*(-A-(98-76-5))^*(4+32^*1)$
8357	14323	$1-2^*(-3456+78-9AB)$	$-BA+9+8765+4-321$
8358	14324	$12-3^*45^*-6^*(-78-(-9A+B))$	$B+A-(-9-8765-(-432-1))$
8359	14325	$-1+2345-6+7-8^*9A^*-B$	$-B-(A-9)-(-8^*-7^*(65+43)^*-2-1)$
835A	14326	$1-2345^*(6-7)+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A+9-(-8765+432)+1$
835B	14327	$1+2345-6+7-8^*-9A^*B$	$B-A^*-987-(-6-54^*(-3-2)^*-1)$
8360	14328	$12+3-4^*-56-(7+89A^*)^*-B$	$-BA-98-7+6^*54^*32+1$
8361	14329	$1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^*6^*(7-8)^{\wedge}9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*(-7-6)^*5)^*-4^*(-3^*2-1)$
8362	14330	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7-8^*9+A-B$	$B-A9+8765-(4+321)$
8363	14331	$-1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7+6)^*(-5^*4^{\wedge}3+2)^*1$
8364	14332	$1+2^*345-(-6-789A+B)$	$-B+A9+87^*-6^*(5+4+3-21)$
8365	14333	$12+345+67-89^*-AB$	$-B^*(A9+87+6-543^*2+1)$
8366	14334	$12345-67-8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^*2-1$
8367	14335	$-1-2-(-3+4+56)^*(-78+9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^*2^*1$
8368	14336	$1-2^*(-345+6)+789A+B$	$-BA9+8^*765+4321$
8369	14337	$1^*-23^*(-4-5^*67+8-9-AB)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7/6-5^*-4^*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
836A	14338	$-1^*(-2345-6-7-8^*9A^*B)$	$-BA-9-(8+7)^*(-654-32)-1$
836B	14339	$12-34+5^*67-89A^*-B$	$-BA+9876-543^*(2+1)$
8370	14340	$-1^*(-2-3-4^{\wedge}5^*(6+7-(8-9)))+A-B$	$-B-(A-9876-(-54^*32-1))$
8371	14341	$1-2-(34+567^*(-8-9+A-B))$	$-BA-98+7-6^*54^*32^*-1$
8372	14342	$1+2^*3+4^{\wedge}5^*(6+7-8+9)+A-B$	$BA^*(9-8-7+6-(-54-32+1))$
8373	14343	$-1+23^*-4-567+89AB$	$-B-A+9^*8^*7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2))^{\wedge}1$
8374	14344	$-1+234+5+6^*7+89A^*B$	$B^*(-A+987-65-4-3-2+1)$
8375	14345	$1-23^*4-567+89AB$	$-B-A+9+(-8+(7/(6-5))^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2-1$
8376	14346	$-1+2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5^*(-6+7-8)+9)+A-B$	$B-A^*-987-6^*-54-32-1$
8377	14347	$123-4+5^*6^*7-89A^*B$	$-BA+9876-5^*(4+321)$
8378	14348	$1+(-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6(6-5)^{\wedge}4(3+2-1)$
8379	14349	$-12-3^*-4^*(5-67)+89AB$	$-B-(A9+87)-6^*-54^*-32^*-1$
837A	14350	$-12-3^*(-4+5)^*-6^*7^*(-8-9+AB)$	$B+A-9^*8+((-7-6)^*(-5-4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
837B	14351	$-1-2^*34+56^*7+89A^*B$	$-B-A+(-9-8+(-7^*(6-5))^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2/1$
8380	14352	$-1^*2^*3^*(-4-5-(678+9AB))$	$B+A+(9+8)^*(7^*-6^*-5^*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8381	14353	$1234-56-(-789-A)^*B$	$BA98-76^*(54+3+2)-1$
8382	14354	$12+34^*-5^*(-67+8)-(-9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*(-7-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^*2-1$
8383	14355	$1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4+5-6)^*7+8+9-(A-B)$	$-B-A^*-987-(65+4-321)$
8384	14356	$-1+234+56-7+89A^*B$	$-BA-(-9+87+6^*54^*32^*-1)$
8385	14357	$1^*234+56-7+89A^*B$	$-BA+9-87+6^*-54^*-32+1$
8386	14358	$-1+2^*(345+6)+789A+B$	$-BA+98^*(7+6^*-5+4^*(32-1))$
8387	14359	$-1-2^*345+67+89AB$	$B+A98^*7+6^*54^*3^*(2+1)$
8388	14360	$1+2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5^*(-6+7-8)+9)+A-B$	$-B+A-(-9876+54^*32)-1$
8389	14361	$1+2^*-345+67+89AB$	$-B+A+9876-54^*-32^*-1$
838A	14362	$-12-(-345+67-89A^*B)$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(54^*32-1)$
838B	14363	$-1-23^*4^*(56-78-9A+B)$	$B-A+9876+54^*32^*-1$
8390	14364	$-1^*(-23+45-6^*-7+8)^*9^*(-A-B)$	$-BA-9^*8^*7^*-6^*5-432^*1$
8391	14365	$1+2-3-45^*-6-(-7-89A)^*B$	$B+A+9+(-8-(7-(6-5)))/-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$
8392	14366	$-1+2+34^*-5^*-67-8-9AB$	$B^*(A-987-65^*(4-(32+1)))$
8393	14367	$-12+34^*5^*67+8-9AB$	$B+A+9-((-8-(7-(6-5)))/4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
8394	14368	$-1+2345-67^*(8-9-AB)$	$-B-A-9-8-7^*6^*(5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8395	14369	$-1-2^*(-345+6)^*(-78+9A-B)$	$B-A^*9-(-8765+4+321)$
8396	14370	$-1+234+56+7+89A^*B$	$B+A-9+(-8+(7/(6-5))^{\wedge}4)^*-3^*-2^*1$
8397	14371	$-1+234-5+67-89A^*B$	$B-A-(-9-8^*76^*5^*4+32+1)$
8398	14372	$-1-2+3^*4^*(-56-7)+89AB$	$B+A+(9-(8+(-7+6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^*-3^*2-1$
8399	14373	$1+234-5+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*8^*(7-(-6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
839A	14374	$1^*-2+345-67-89A^*-B$	$-B+A^*-9-8^*-76^*-5^*-4-3^*-21$
839B	14375	$1^*(23-4)^*5^*(6-7+89+A+B)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7+(-6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)+2/1$
83A0	14376	$-1-23+456+7-89^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7+6)^*(-5^*4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
83A1	14377	$-1^*(2+34-5-(6-7)^*89A)^*-B$	$B^*(-A9+876-54^*-3-2^*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
83A2	14378	$1-23+456+7-89^*-AB$	$B-A^*-987+6^*54+3^*-2-1$
83A3	14379	$-123-4+567+89^*AB$	$B+A^*987-6+54^*3^*-2^*-1$
83A4	14380	$1-2^*(3-(4^5+6))^*7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7-6+5)^*(4^4(3+2)+1)$
83A5	14381	$-1+234+5+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8^*(-7-6)^*(5-4^43)^*2-1$
83A6	14382	$1^*2^*(3-4^*567+8^*-9A^*-B)$	$B+A+9876+54^*-32-1$
83A7	14383	$-1^*(2+34-567)^*(8-(-9+A)^*-B)$	$B+A^*-9^*(-87-65)+4^*-321$
83A8	14384	$-1-(2+3)+456-(7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A+9876+54^*-32+1$
83A9	14385	$1+2^*-3-(-456+7)-89^*-AB$	$BA+9^*876+5^*(432-1)$
83AA	14386	$1-2-3+456-7+89^*AB$	$B+A-9^*-8^*-7^*-6^*(-5/4+3^*2)+1$
83AB	14387	$-123+4+567-89^*-AB$	$-BA-(-9876-5^*(4-321))$
83B0	14388	$-1+2^*(3+4567)-89^*A+B$	$-B^*(-A-987+65-4+3+21)$
83B1	14389	$12+3^*4^*(-56-7)+89AB$	$-B+A^*(9-8)^*-76^*(-5-4^*3+2-1)$
83B2	14390	$1+2-3+456-7-89^*-AB$	$BA+9^*876-5^*432^*-1$
83B3	14391	$1-2^*3^*(4+5-67)+89A^*B$	$B+A+9^*(-8^*(7-(-6+5^4)/3)+2)^{\wedge}1$
83B4	14392	$1-2+3+456-7+89^*AB$	$B+A+(-9-8+(-7^*(6-5))^4)^*3^*2-1$
83B5	14393	$-12+3+456+7+89^*AB$	$B+A+(-9-8+(-7^*(6-5))^4)^*3^*2+1$
83B6	14394	$-1+2-(-3-456+7+89^*-AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+(-7^*(6-5))^4)^*3^*2+1$
83B7	14395	$1+2-34+56^*7-89A^*-B$	$BA+9^*876-5^*(-432-1)$
83B8	14396	$-1^*-2^*(3-4+56)^*(7+8-(-9A+B))$	$B+A^*9+8765-432^*1$
83B9	14397	$-1-2-34^*(-5-6+7-8)^*(9+A+B)$	$B+A-9+(-8-7)^*(6^*-5/(-4^4-3^*2)+1)$
83BA	14398	$-12-34-567+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-(-8+(7/(6-5))^4)^*3)^*-2+1$
83BB	14399	$1234-5+6^*(-7+89)^*(A+B)$	$-B+A+9-8^*-76^*5^*4-3^*(2+1)$
8400	14400	$1-2-(3-(456+7)+89^*-AB)$	$-B-A^*-987-6^*-54+32-1$
8401	14401	$12-(3-456+7-89^*AB)$	$-B+A9^*87+(6-(-5-4))^*-3^*-21$
8402	14402	$1-23-4+56^*7-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*((-8+7+6)^*-5^*4^43+2)-1$
8403	14403	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*((-8+7+6)^*-5^*4^43+2^{\wedge}1)$
8404	14404	$1+2-3+456+7-89^*-AB$	$-B-A^*9^*(-87+6-54)^*3^*-21$
8405	14405	$-1^*(2-3-456-7+89^*-AB)$	$-B-A+9876-54^*(32-1)$
8406	14406	$-12^*(345-67-8-9AB)$	$-B-A-9^*((-8-7)^*-6-5^4)^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
8407	14407	$-1-23^*-4-5^*(-67+89)^*-A^*B$	$-B-A-9^*((-8-7)^*-6-5^4)^*3+2+1$
8408	14408	$-1+2+3-(-456-7)+89^*AB$	$-BA9-8-7^*-6^*-54^*-3^*2+1$
8409	14409	$-1-2-34-(567-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9+(8+(-7+6)^5)^4)^*3^*2/1$
840A	14410	$1^*(2+3-4-(-5-6-(-7+89)))^*AB$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(-876-54-3-2+1)$
840B	14411	$1-2-34-(567-89AB)$	$-BA+98^*76-(-5-4)^*321$
8410	14412	$1-2+345-6^*7+89A^*B$	$-B-(-A9-8765)-(432+1)$
8411	14413	$-1+2-(-34+567-89AB)$	$-B+A9+8765+432^*-1$
8412	14414	$12+3^*4^*(-56+7+89A-B)$	$-B+A9-(-8765+432-1)$
8413	14415	$1+2-(34+567-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7^*-6-5^4)^*-3^*-2^*1$
8414	14416	$1+2+345+6^*-7+89A^*B$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7^*-6-5^4)^*3^*2+1$
8415	14417	$-12+3-4-56^*-7-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9+(8-(-7-6)^5)^4)^*3^*2-1$
8416	14418	$1+23+456-7-89^*-AB$	$B-A^*(-987+6)+5^*4+321$
8417	14419	$1-2-3^*4-56^*-7-89A^*-B$	$B+A98+(-7-65)^*-43^*(2+1)$
8418	14420	$-1-23-4-567+89AB$	$B+A+(9^*8+7^*6+5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8419	14421	$-1^*(23+4+567-89AB)$	$B^*(A9+876-(54-3-2+1))$
841A	14422	$1-23-4-567+89AB$	$B+A+(9+8-7)^{\wedge}6/5^4)^*3^*2+1$
841B	14423	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7+6)^*-5^*4^43+2^{\wedge}1$
8420	14424	$1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+98^*-7^*6+543^*21$
8421	14425	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6/7+8+9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876+54^*(-32+1)$
8422	14426	$12-34-567+89AB$	$-B-A-9+8765+4-321$
8423	14427	$-1-2^*-3^*-4-(567-89AB)$	$BA-9+8765-(432+1)$
8424	14428	$-12+345-6-7+89A^*B$	$BA-9+8765-432^*1$
8425	14429	$1^*-23+4-567+89AB$	$BA-9+8765-432+1$
8426	14430	$1-23+4-567+89AB$	$B+A+9+(8^*7^{\wedge}4(6-5)+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
8427	14431	$-123-(456+7-89AB)$	$B-A^*(-987-(6+5)-4-3-21)$
8428	14432	$-1^*-234^*(5-(-6-7)-(-89-AB))$	$B^*(A+987-(-6+54)-(-32+1))$
8429	14433	$123-4^*(-56-7)+89A^*B$	$B+A+(9-8+(-7^*(6-5))^4)^*-3^*-2^*1$
842A	14434	$-123+456-7+89A^*B$	$B-(-A9-8765)-432-1$
842B	14435	$((1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6^*(7-8)^{\wedge}9+A-B$	$B+A9-(-8765+432^*1)$
8430	14436	$-1+23-(45-6-7+89A^*)^*-B$	$B+A9+8765-432+1$
8431	14437	$-12+3-4-567+89AB$	$-B+A9^*-8^*(7-(-6+54)-(-32+1))$
8432	14438	$-1-23+(-4-5)^*-67-89^*-AB$	$-B+A-9+8765-4-321$
8433	14439	$-12-3-(-4+567)+89AB$	$B-A-9^*((-8+7+6)^*-5^*4^43-2^{\wedge}1)$
8434	14440	$-1-234+567+89A^*B$	$B-(A+9-(8765-4))-321$
8435	14441	$-1+2-3^*4-(567-89AB)$	$-B-A^*-987+65^*(4+3-2+1)$
8436	14442	$1-234+567+89A^*B$	$-BA-9+8-7+6^*-54^*32^*-1$
8437	14443	$-1^*(-23-4-5-(-67-89A))^*-B$	$B^*(A-(9-876-54-3^*2^*1))$
8438	14444	$1-2-3-4-567+89AB$	$-B-(A-9-8765)-(-4+321)$
8439	14445	$12-34^*-5^*6-(-78-9)^*AB$	$BA+9+8765-432-1$
843A	14446	$-1+2-(3+4)-(567-89AB)$	$-B+A-(9-8765)+4-321$
843B	14447	$12-3+4+56^*7-89A^*-B$	$B+A9-(-8765+432-1)$
8440	14448	$1+2-3-4-567+89AB$	$B-A-9+8765+4-321$
8441	14449	$-1-2^*3+4-567+89AB$	$B+A-9+8^*-76^*5^*-4+32-1$
8442	14450	$-1-2-3+4-567+89AB$	$-B-A^*-987-(-654+321)$
8443	14451	$1^*-2-3+4-(567-89AB)$	$B+A9+87+6^*-54^*(-32+1)$
8444	14452	$1-2-(3-4+567-89AB)$	$B+A+9-(-8^*76^*-5^*-4+3-21)$
8445	14453	$-1^*(2-345-(6-7)^*89A^*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*(-7^*-6^*-5^*4-3^*2)-1$
8446	14454	$1+2+3-4-567+89AB$	$-B^*(-A98-7-6+5^*-43^*(-2+1))$
8447	14455	$1-(2-345)-6-(-7+89A^*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7)^*-6^*-5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
8448	14456	$12+345-6-7+89A^*B$	$-B+A+9+8765-4-321$
8449	14457	$-12-3^*-4^*5^*(-6-7)+89AB$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7^*(-6+5/4)^*3^*2+1)$
844A	14458	$-1+2^*-3^*(45+67)+89AB$	$B-(A-(9-(-8765+4)))^*-321$
844B	14459	$12-(3+4+567-89AB)$	$-B-A-(9+87)+6^*54^*32^*1$
8450	14460	$-1-234+56^*-7+89AB$	$-B-A-9-87-6^*-54^*32+1$
8451	14461	$-1-(2-3^*4-(-567+89AB))$	$B+A-9+(8^*7-6)/(5^*4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8452	14462	$1-234-56^*7+89AB$	$B-A^*(-987+6)+54+321$
8453	14463	$1+2+3^*4^*(-56+78-9^*-AB)$	$B+A-9+(8+7^*6)^*(5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
8454	14464	$-1^*(2-3-4^{\wedge}5^*(6-7/8+9))+A-B$	$-B+A+9+8765+4-321$
8455	14465	$12+3-4-567+89AB$	$B+A-9+(-8/(7(6-5)))^{\wedge}4)^*-3^*2-1$
8456	14466	$-1-(2+3^*-45^*(-6-7-(-89-A)-B))$	$B-A+9+8765-(-4+321)$
8457	14467	$12-3-(-4+567-89AB)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*-7^*(-6^*5+4/3)-2^*1$
8458	14468	$12+345-(-6+7)+89A^*B$	$B+A-9-(-8765-4+321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8459	14469	$12+345+(-6+7)*89A*B$	$-B-(A9-8765-4*-3*21)$
845A	14470	$12+345-(6-(7-89A*-B))$	$-B+A*987+6*5-(-4-321)$
845B	14471	$1-(-2-345-6)-(-7+89A*-B)$	$-BA9+8765-43*-21$
8460	14472	$1+2+3+(-4-5)*-67+89*AB$	$B+A*987+654-321$
8461	14473	$12+3+4-(567-89AB)$	$BA9-8-(7+65)*4*32*-1$
8462	14474	$-1+23-(4+567)+89AB$	$B+A-9*(8+(-7*(6-5))^4)/-3*2-1$
8463	14475	$1+2*-34+567-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9*((-8-7)*-6-5^4)+3)*(2+1)$
8464	14476	$1+23-4-567+89AB$	$B*(A9-(-876+5)-(43-2+1))$
8465	14477	$-1+234-5*-67+89*AB$	$B+A9-(8*7*(-65-43)*2-1)$
8466	14478	$-12+34-567+89AB$	$-B+A-(9+87+6*-54*32+1)$
8467	14479	$1+234+5*67-89*-AB$	$-B+A*9-8*-76*5*4-3+2+1$
8468	14480	$1+2+(3+4)^5*6/7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7*6)*(5*4-3)^2*1$
8469	14481	$12+345*6+7+89*-A*-B$	$-B+A98+7*-65*(4-(3+2+1))$
846A	14482	$-1+23+4-567+89AB$	$B-A-(-9876-543*(-2-1))$
846B	14483	$-1*(-23-4-(-567+89AB))$	$-BA-9*(8-7)*(65-4*3)*-21$
8470	14484	$1+23+4-567+89AB$	$BA*(9-8-(7-6)-(-54+32*-1))$
8471	14485	$1234+56-(789+A)*-B$	$B-A-(98-(7+6*54*32+1))$
8472	14486	$1-2*(3-(4^5+6)*7)+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8765+4-321$
8473	14487	$(1*2*3+4*5)*(6+7*8)*9-(A+B)$	$B*(A98-7-(-6+54)*(3+2-1))$
8474	14488	$-1+(-2+3/4+5*6)*-7*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7/6*(5+4)^3-2^1-1)$
8475	14489	$-1-2+34-567+89AB$	$-B-A-9*(8+7)+(6+5)^4+3+2-1$
8476	14490	$12*(3-(45-678)+9A+B)$	$B-A+9876+5*(-4-321)$
8477	14491	$1-2+34-567+89AB$	$B-A9+8765+4*-3*21$
8478	14492	$12345+67-8*-9A*-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7+6+5)*-4*3*2-1$
8479	14493	$-1-(-2-34)-(-567-89AB)$	$-B+A*987-65*(-4-3)-21$
847A	14494	$1*2+34-567+89AB$	$-B+A98-(-7654+3*21)$
847B	14495	$1+2+34-(567-89AB)$	$-B+A*(9+8*-7)+6*54*(32+1)$
8480	14496	$1-(2+3)^4+5^6*7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A9*87-65-43*-21$
8481	14497	$-1*-2*(3+(4^5+6)*7)+8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+9-87-6*54*-32*1$
8482	14498	$-1*2*(-345-(67+89-A))*B$	$-B*(-A9-876+5-(-43+2)-1)$
8483	14499	$-1234-5-6*78*(-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9*8-7*6*(5-4*3)^2(2+1)$
8484	14500	$-1*-2*(3-45)*(-6-7-(-8-(-9-AB)))$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6*5^4)^3(3-2+1)$
8485	14501	$1*2+(3+4)^5*6/7+8*9+A+B$	$B+A-9-87+6*54*-32*-1$
8486	14502	$((1+2*3)^4+5)*6+7*8+9-(A-B)$	$-B-A9*-8-(-7654-321)$
8487	14503	$-1+(-2-3^4)*((5*-6+7)*8+9)-(A+B)$	$BA+9876+54*-32-1$
8488	14504	$12*(-3-(-4-(567+89+AB)))$	$BA+9876-54*-32*-1$
8489	14505	$-12-34*5*67-89A-B$	$BA-(-9876+54*32-1)$
848A	14506	$12-(-34+567)+89AB$	$-B-A+(-9-8)*7+(6+5)^4+3+2*1$
848B	14507	$(1*2*3+4*5)*(6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)*7+(6+5)^4+3+2+1$
8490	14508	$-1*2*(-3-4*-5*6)*(-78+9+A+B)$	$-B-A9+8*7-6*54*-32*1$
8491	14509	$-1234+5-6*-78*(9+A+B)$	$-B+A*9*87-6*-5*(4-3)*-21$
8492	14510	$-1-2^3*(4+(-5*-6*-7+8)*9)+A-B$	$BA-9+(8+7)*654+321$
8493	14511	$1-23*-4*5-(6-7)*89A*B$	$B+A*(987+65-4+3-21)$
8494	14512	$-12-(-345+6)-(-7-89A)*B$	$B-A*(9+8)*(-76+5)-43*(-2+1)$
8495	14513	$1-(2+34-567)+89*AB$	$BA+9-(8*76*5*-4+32*1)$
8496	14514	$1*2*(-3-4+56)*(-7+8-9+AB)$	$-B-A-9*8-7+(6+5)^4-3^1(2+1)$
8497	14515	$-12-3+45*-6-(7-8)*-9A*-B$	$-B+A*-9-8-(7+6-5)*4*-321$
8498	14516	$-1+(-2^3-3^4+5+6)*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A98-(-7654+3*21)$
8499	14517	$1+2-(34-567-89*AB)$	$-B+A*987-65+432+1$
849A	14518	$12*(3+4-(-5-6-78)*(9-A+B))$	$B+A9*8-7*65*(4-3)*-21$
849B	14519	$(-1+2-(3-4*-5*6))*-7*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$B+A+9-(87+6*54*-32*1)$
84A0	14520	$-12-(-345-67)-89A*-B$	$B*(A-(-9-87+65+43*-21))$
84A1	14521	$1-2*(3+456+7+8)*(9-A)*B$	$-B+A9*87+6*-5+43*21$
84A2	14522	$-1-23-4-(-567+89*-AB)$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+(6+5)^4-3*2+1$
84A3	14523	$-1+(-2-3^4)*((5*-6+7)*8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9-8*-76*5*4-(3+2+1)$
84A4	14524	$-1+2*(-3+(-4-5)*-6*(7+8))*9+A-B$	$BA+9*8*7-6*543*(-2-1)$
84A5	14525	$(-1-2-(-3/-4-5*6)*7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7*-654+321$
84A6	14526	$-1*2*(-3*4+56*-78-9*AB)$	$-B-(A98-7*(-6-5*(-4-321)))$
84A7	14527	$-1-234-5*67+89AB$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+(6+5)^4*(3-2^1)$
84A8	14528	$1*-234-5*67+89AB$	$B-A*-987+6-(-54-321)$
84A9	14529	$1-234-5*67+89AB$	$B+A+9*(8*7+6)*(5*4+3*2*1)$
84AA	14530	$-1-(23-4)+567-89*-AB$	$-B+A98+7654-(32+1)$
84AB	14531	$-1-(2-345)-(-67-89A*B)$	$-B+A98+7654+32*-1$
84B0	14532	$123-4-5*-67-89A*-B$	$-B+A98+7654-32+1$
84B1	14533	$-12-3-(4-567)-89*-AB$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*6+5)*(4+3)^2-1$
84B2	14534	$1-2*(-3-(4^5+6))*7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7-6*5)*(4+3)^2*1$
84B3	14535	$-1+2+345+67-89A*-B$	$-B-A+98+(76+5)*4*32*1$
84B4	14536	$-1*(-2-345-67+89A*-B)$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+(6+5)^4+3^2*1$
84B5	14537	$1+2+345+67-89A*-B$	$BA98+76*(-54-3)-(-2-1)$
84B6	14538	$1-2-3+(45+6-7+89A)*B$	$B-A*-987-65-432*-1$
84B7	14539	$-12+3-4+567+89*AB$	$B+A9-8*-76*5*-4*(-3+2)-1$
84B8	14540	$123+4+5*67+89A*B$	$B+A9-8*-76*-5*-4+3-2-1$
84B9	14541	$-12+34*5*-6-(-789A+B)$	$-B+A98-(-7654+3+21)$
84BA	14542	$-1+(-2^3*-4*-5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B*(A9-(-876-5)-43-(2+1))$
84BB	14543	$-1-(23+45*-67)+8*9A*B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7+(6+5)^4-3+2+1$
8500	14544	$-1-(-234-56*7-89*AB)$	$BA-98*-7+6*5*(-4+321)$
8501	14545	$1-(23-45*67-8*-9A*-B)$	$BA+98*7*6+543*21$
8502	14546	$1+234-56*-7-89*-AB$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5+4^3+2)-1$
8503	14547	$-12+3+4-(-567-89*AB)$	$-B-(-A98-7654)-(-3+2+1)$
8504	14548	$12+345+67+89A*B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7+(6+5)^4+3+2*1$
8505	14549	$1-((-2+3^4)*(5*-6+7)*8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-6-(5+4)*321$
8506	14550	$-1-(2-3)-(4-567)-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9*-8*-7+6^5-4-3)*2-1$
8507	14551	$-12+3-45*(6+7)+89AB$	$B+A98*7-6*(5-432+1)$
8508	14552	$1*-2-3*-4*56+7+89*AB$	$B-(-A98-7654+32)-1$
8509	14553	$-1*(2-3-4*5-6)*7*(8+9-A)*B$	$-B*(A-9)*(-876-5-43-21)$
850A	14554	$-1+2+3-4+567+89*AB$	$B-(-A98-7654-(-32+1))$
850B	14555	$-1*(-2-3+4-567-89*AB)$	$-B-(A9-87+6*54*32*-1)$
8510	14556	$1+2345-(-67-8)*(-9+AB)$	$B+A98*7-6*(5-432)-1$
8511	14557	$1+2*-3-45*(6+7)+89AB$	$B-A98*7+6*(-5+432*1)$
8512	14558	$1*(2-3)*(-4-(567-89*-AB))$	$-BA+98-(-7+6*-54*32+1)$
8513	14559	$-1+23*4-(567-89AB)$	$B+A98+7*-654*(-3-(-2+1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8514	14560	$-12+3+45*67+8*9A*B$	$-BA+9*87*6-5*4*-321$
8515	14561	$123+456-7-89*-AB$	$-B-A98-7*6*54*-3*-2*-1$
8516	14562	$-1-2-(-3-45*(-6-7)-89AB)$	$-B+A98-765*-4*3-2-1$
8517	14563	$1-(-2^A(3^4+5)+6+7-8)/9+A-B$	$-B-(-A98-(7654+3*-2*1))$
8518	14564	$1+2+3+4+567-89*-AB$	$-B+A98+7654-3*2+1$
8519	14565	$-1*(2+3)*(-45+(67-89)*-A*-B)$	$-B-(-A98-7654)-(3+2)+1$
851A	14566	$-1*(2+3-45*67-8*9A*B)$	$-B+A9+8765-4-321$
851B	14567	$12+3-4+567+89*AB$	$-B+A98+7654-3+2-1$
8520	14568	$12-3*-4*56+7-89*-AB$	$BA+9876+54*(-32+1)$
8521	14569	$12-(3-4)+567+89*AB$	$B-(-A98-7654-3+21)$
8522	14570	$1-2*(-3-(4^A+5)*7-8*9)+A-B$	$-B+A98-(-7654*(3-2)-1)$
8523	14571	$1-(-2+3+45*-67)-8*-9A*B$	$-B-(-A98-7654-3-(-2+1))$
8524	14572	$(-1-2*3)*-4*-5*(-6-7)*8-9+A+B$	$-B+A98+7654+3*(2-1)$
8525	14573	$12-3-45*(6+7)+89AB$	$-B+A98+7654+3+2-1$
8526	14574	$-1-23-456-7+89AB$	$-B+A98+7654+3+2*1$
8527	14575	$123+456+7-89*-AB$	$B*(A+9-876-54-32)*-1$
8528	14576	$1-(23+456)-(-7-89AB)$	$-B+A98+7654-3*-2+1$
8529	14577	$-1-(23-456-(-7-89A*-B))$	$B-A9+87+6*-54*32*-1$
852A	14578	$-1*(23-456+7+89A*-B)$	$B+A-9*8-7+(6+5)^A4-3-2/1$
852B	14579	$1-23+456-7-89A*-B$	$-B-A-9+8765-4*-3*-21$
8530	14580	$-1*(2+3)*-4*(-56-7-8)*9*(A-B)$	$B+A-9*8-7+(6+5)^A4-3^A(2-1)$
8531	14581	$1*2+3/4*5*6^A7/8/9+A-B$	$BA-9+8765-4-321$
8532	14582	$12-3-45*-67+8*9A*B$	$B+A-9*8-7+(6+5)^A4-3+2/1$
8533	14583	$-1*2^A3-4^A5*(-6*7/8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A*-987-6-5+432+1$
8534	14584	$-1+23-(-4-567)-89*-AB$	$B-(-A98-7654+3*2+1)$
8535	14585	$-12-(3+456+7)+89AB$	$B+A98+7654-3-(2+1)$
8536	14586	$-1+23-4*(-56+78)*(-9-AB)$	$-B*(-A9+87)*(-6+5+43+2-1)$
8537	14587	$-1+2-3*(456+7)*-8+9*-A*B$	$B+A98+765*4*-3*(-2+1)$
8538	14588	$-12-3-(-456+7)+89A*B$	$B+A9+8765-4-321$
8539	14589	$-1*(23+456-(-7+89AB))$	$BA-9+8765-(-4+321)$
853A	14590	$1-23-456+7+89AB$	$-BA-98*(76-54*3-21)$
853B	14591	$-12+3-456-7+89AB$	$B+A98+7654+3-(2+1)$
8540	14592	$-1*(23-456-7+89A*-B)$	$-BA-98-76*5*(4-32+1)$
8541	14593	$1-2-(-34-567+89*-AB)$	$B-(-A98-7654)+3-(2-1)$
8542	14594	$-123-4+567+89A*B$	$B+A-9-8*7+(6+5)^A4-3*(2-1)$
8543	14595	$-12-3+4*567-8*-9AB$	$B+A98-(-7654-3)-(-2+1)$
8544	14596	$-1-2-3-456-7+89AB$	$B+A9+8765+4-321$
8545	14597	$-1-23-45-(-6+(7+89)*-AB)$	$-B+A98+7654+3+21$
8546	14598	$1-(2+3-(-456-7+89AB))$	$B+A-9-8*7+(6+5)^A4+3-2/1$
8547	14599	$-12-(3+456)-(-7-89AB)$	$BA+9+8765-4-321$
8548	14600	$-1*(-2+3)*4*-5*(-6+7*89-A+B)$	$B+A98+7654+3*(2+1)$
8549	14601	$-12+3-4*-567+8*9AB$	$B+A-9-8*7+(6+5)^A4+3+2-1$
854A	14602	$-12-3+456-(-7+89A*-B)$	$B+A-9-8*7+(6+5)^A4+3+2/1$
854B	14603	$-1+2-3+456-7+89A*B$	$-B-A*(-987-6+5)+432*1$
8550	14604	$1-2+3-456-7+89AB$	$B+A*987-6-5+432*1$
8551	14605	$-12-(-3+456)-(-7-89AB)$	$-BA-9+8765+4*-32-1$
8552	14606	$-1-(-2-(3-456))-(-7-89AB)$	$-B+A98+7654+32-1$
8553	14607	$123+4+56*7-89A*-B$	$B+A+9+8765+4-321$
8554	14608	$12-(-34-567)+89*AB$	$-B+A98+7654+32+1$
8555	14609	$-1+2*-3-(456-7-89AB)$	$B+A987+65*(-43+2*-1)$
8556	14610	$-1-2-3-456+7+89AB$	$B+A987+65*(-43-2)+1$
8557	14611	$1+2+3+456-7+89A*B$	$BA-98-7+6*54*-32*-1$
8558	14612	$-1-2*3-(-456-7)-89A*-B$	$B+A98+765*4*3+21$
8559	14613	$12-3-456-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8765-4*(32+1)$
855A	14614	$-1+2-3-456+7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5)^A4-3+2*1$
855B	14615	$1-(2+3-456-7)-89A*-B$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5)^A4-3+2+1$
8560	14616	$1+2-3-(456-7-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8765-(-4*-32+1)$
8561	14617	$-1*(2-3+456-7-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8765-4*-32*-1$
8562	14618	$1-2+3-456+7+89AB$	$-B-A9-(-8765+4*32)+1$
8563	14619	$123-4-(567-89AB)$	$B+A98-(-7654-3-21)$
8564	14620	$-1+2+3-456+7+89AB$	$-B+A*(987+6+5+43+2)+1$
8565	14621	$-1*(-2-3-(-456+7+89AB))$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5)^A4+3*2*1$
8566	14622	$12+3+456-7+89A*B$	$BA-9-87-6*-54*-32*-1$
8567	14623	$12-(3+4*-567)+8*9AB$	$BA-9-87+6*-54*-32+1$
8568	14624	$(-1+(-2-3+4+5*6)*-7*8)*-9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8765-4*-32*-1$
8569	14625	$-12+3456-7*(-89A+B)$	$-B+A-(-98-76)*(-5+43+21)$
856A	14626	$12345-6-7*(8+9AB)$	$BA*(-9-8-(7*(-6-5)-(-4-(-32-1))))$
856B	14627	$123+4-567+89AB$	$-BA+987*6+5*-43*-21$
8570	14628	$-1+23-456-7+89AB$	$B+A98+7654+32-1$
8571	14629	$1*23-456-(-7-89AB)$	$B-(-A98-7654)-32*-1$
8572	14630	$-1*2*(-3-4*(5-6))*7*(-89A)*B$	$B+A98+7654+32+1$
8573	14631	$-1+23*-4*5-67+89AB$	$B+A9+(8+7)*(654+32)+1$
8574	14632	$12+3-4-(56-7+89A)*-B$	$-BA+987*(6+5)-432-1$
8575	14633	$12+3-456-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9-8-7+(6+5)^A4-3-2*1$
8576	14634	$1-(-2-(-3-4-5*-6*7)*8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+987*(6+5)-432+1$
8577	14635	$1-2+(-3-4*5*6)*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-A-9*(-876-54*-3*2*-1)$
8578	14636	$12+3+456+7-89A*-B$	$B+A-9-8-7+(6+5)^A4-3+2-1$
8579	14637	$1234+5-(67+8+9)*-AB$	$B+A-98*(7+6-54-3*21)$
857A	14638	$-1+23-(4*-567-8*9AB)$	$B+A+9+8765+4*-32-1$
857B	14639	$(1-2+3*4)^(5+6-7)+8-9+A-B$	$B-A9+8765-4*-32*-1$
8580	14640	$1+23+4*567-8*-9AB$	$B-A9-(-8765+4*32-1)$
8581	14641	$-12-(3+4*5-6-(-7+89)*AB)$	$-B*(-A9+8)*7-(-6+5*-4)+3-2(1)$
8582	14642	$-1+23-456+7+89AB$	$B+A*(987+6+5-(-43-2))+1$
8583	14643	$1*23-456+7+89AB$	$B-(-A9-8765-4*(-32+1))$
8584	14644	$-12*(3-4)*(-56+789-(-A+B))$	$-B-(-A98-7654+3*-21)$
8585	14645	$-1+23+456+7+89A*B$	$B+A*987-(-6*5-432)*1$
8586	14646	$-1*(-23-456-7-89A*B)$	$-BA-9+8765-4*(3+21)$
8587	14647	$1+23-(-456-7)+89A*B$	$-B+A*(987+65)+43*2*-1$
8588	14648	$-12-34+5*6-(7+89)*-AB$	$BA+9*-8*-7*-6*-5+432*-1$
8589	14649	$1+2345*6-(-78*-9-A)*B$	$B+A+9-8-7+(6+5)^A4-3*2-1$
858A	14650	$(-1*-2-(-3-4*5*6)*7)*(8+9)-(A+B)$	$-B-A*(-987-6-54+3)-(-2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
858B	14651	$1234-5-6*(7+8)*(-9-AB)$	$B+A+9-8-7+(6+5)^4-3-2^4$
8590	14652	$(1-(2+3+4)^5)/(6+7-8-9)-A*B$	$-B*(A9-87+6+5)^{-4}3*(2+1)$
8591	14653	$12+3456-7*(-89A+B)$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5)^4-3^2*1$
8592	14654	$-1-(-2+(-3+4-5*6)*7*8)*9+A+B$	$BA9-8+7654-3*21$
8593	14655	$(-1+2-(-3-4*5*6)*7)*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$-BA-9+8765+43*2-1$
8594	14656	$-1*(2+3+45+6)*(7-89-AB)$	$-BA-9+8765+43*2*1$
8595	14657	$(1-2+3^4)^5(5+6-7)+8+9+A-B$	$BA9-(8-7*65*4*3*2*1)$
8596	14658	$12*(3-4-(-56-789+AB))$	$B+A+9-8-7+(6+5)^4+3-2+1$
8597	14659	$1^2+(-3-4*5*6)*-7*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A*9*(-8-(-76-5-43-21))$
8598	14660	$-1*(2-(-34-5*6)-(7+89)*AB)$	$B+A+9-8-7+(6+5)^4+3+2-1$
8599	14661	$(1-2+3^4)^5(5+6-7)+8-9+A+B$	$-B+A9*87-(-654-321)$
859A	14662	$1+23*-4-(-567+89A*-B)$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5)^4+3-2-1$
859B	14663	$1-2*-3*-4*(-5-6)*7*8+9-AB$	$-B*(A+98-(-76+5))*(-4-32-1)$
85A0	14664	$((1+2+3)^4)^5(5-6*7*8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5)^4+3-2+1$
85A1	14665	$-1+2-3*-4*(-5*6-(7-89A+B))$	$B+A+9-8-7+(6+5)^4+3^2*1$
85A2	14666	$-12+3-4*56*7-8-9A+B$	$B+A98+7654-3*21$
85A3	14667	$-12+3456-7*(89A)*-B$	$-B-A9+8765+43*2*1$
85A4	14668	$-1+23*-4*5*6*7+89AB$	$-B-(A9-8765-43*2)+1$
85A5	14669	$(-1-2*3^4)/-5*(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A*987-(-65-432)-1$
85A6	14670	$(-1*-2-(-3-4*5*6)*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8-(-7654+3*21)$
85A7	14671	$-1-23*(45-67)-89A*-B$	$BA9+8+7*(-654+3)*2*1$
85A8	14672	$-1*-2*(-3-4)*(-56-789+AB)$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6-5)^4+3^2+1$
85A9	14673	$-12-345-(67-89AB)$	$-BA+9*87*6+5432-1$
85AA	14674	$(-1*2-(3+4-56-7-89A))*B$	$-B*(-A-(987-65)-(-4-3-(-2+1)))$
85AB	14675	$(-1+2-(-3-4*5*6)*7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$-BA-(-9-8765)-(-43*2-1)$
85B0	14676	$-1-2-(-3-4*(-5+6)+(7+89)*-AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+(6+5)^4+3+2-1$
85B1	14677	$-1+2-3-4+5-(-6+(7+89)*-AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+(6+5)^4+3+2*1$
85B2	14678	$-12+3+456-(-7-89A)*B$	$-BA-9*8*7*6*5*4*3*2-1$
85B3	14679	$1*(2-3+4)*(-56*7-89*AB)$	$-BA-(9-8765+4)*3*21$
85B4	14680	$-1+23*-4+56*7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5)^4-3*2*1$
85B5	14681	$-123-4-5*67+89AB$	$B+A9*8*-7+65+4321$
85B6	14682	$1*-23+5*-6*7*-8*9-A*B$	$-BA-9+8765-43-21$
85B7	14683	$-1*-2*-3*-4*(-5-6)*-7*8+9-A*B$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5)^4-3*(2-1)$
85B8	14684	$-1-2-345-67+89AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5)^4-3+2-1$
85B9	14685	$-1*(2*3^4+5-6)*(-78+9AB)$	$B*(A-(-987+65)-(-4+3+2*-1))$
85BA	14686	$1-2-345-67+89AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6+5)^4-3+2+1$
85BB	14687	$(-1/-2*-3*-4-5*6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-BA-9-(-8765-4+3*21)$
8600	14688	$-1+2-345-(67-89AB)$	$B-(A9-8765)-(-43*2+1)$
8601	14689	$-123+4-5*67+89AB$	$-B+A9-(8+7)+6*(54*32-1)$
8602	14690	$1+2-345-67+89AB$	$BA9-(8-7654+32+1)$
8603	14691	$1+2*(3456+78+9AB)$	$BA9-8+7654-32*1$
8604	14692	$-1+23+4*5*6*7-89A*-B$	$BA9-8+7654-32+1$
8605	14693	$-1-23*-4-56*(-78-9A-B)$	$-B-A9+8765-43-21$
8606	14694	$-1+2*(345-6-78)*(9A)-B$	$-B-A+9*(876-(54-321))$
8607	14695	$-1-2-34+56+(-7+89)*AB$	$-B-A+(98-76*5)*(-4-3+21)$
8608	14696	$1-(2-((3*4-5)^6+7)/8)-9A-B$	$B*(A+987-6-54-3*(2-1))$
8609	14697	$((1+2+3-4+5)^6+7)/8-9A-B$	$-BA+9+8765-4+3*21$
860A	14698	$1+((2^3+4-5)^6+7)/8-9A-B$	$-B-A9+8765+4-3*21$
860B	14699	$-1*(2-((-3*4-5)^6+7)/8)-9A-B$	$B+A-9+8*7+(6+5)^4-3^2-1$
8610	14700	$12*(-3+45)^*(6-7-8+9+A+B)$	$-BA-(-9-8765+43)-21$
8611	14701	$12-345-(67-89AB)$	$BA9-8+7654-3-21$
8612	14702	$-1-2345-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A-9+8*7+(6+5)^4-3*2-1$
8613	14703	$(-1/-2*-3-(4-5*6*7))*8*9-(A+B)$	$B-A9+8765+4*(3-21)$
8614	14704	$1-2+3456-7*-89A-B$	$-BA-9-(-8765+43+2+1)$
8615	14705	$(1-2+(3*4-5)^6)/(7-8+9)+A-B$	$-BA-(-9-8765-4)+3*21$
8616	14706	$-1+2+3456+7*89A-B$	$-BA-9-(-8765+43+2-1)$
8617	14707	$-1*(-2-(3456-7*-89A)+B)$	$BA9-8+7654+3-21$
8618	14708	$1-(-2-3456-7*89A+B)$	$BA9+8+7654-32+1$
8619	14709	$-1+23*-4*5+6-7+89AB$	$-BA9-(-8+76*5*(-4+32-1))$
861A	14710	$-12-345-6*7+89AB$	$-BA-(9-8765)-(-43-2-1)$
861B	14711	$-1+23*4*5-(6-7-89AB)$	$BA9+8*7*(-7+65)*(43-21)$
8620	14712	$(1^2-3^4)^5(5+6-7)+8*9+A-B$	$B-A9+8765-4-3*21$
8621	14713	$-12+3456+7*89A+B$	$BA9+8-7*654*(-3-(-2+1))$
8622	14714	$1+2+3+4+5-6-(7+89)*-AB$	$BA98-76*5*(4-3*(-2-1))$
8623	14715	$-12-34+567-89A*-B$	$B-A9-(-8765+43)-21$
8624	14716	$-1*(2-(-345-67))*(89-AB)$	$-B+A987-65*43-21$
8625	14717	$1+23+4-(5+6)*(78-9AB)$	$BA9+8+7654-(3+21)$
8626	14718	$-1-23+4*567-89*A*-B$	$B*(-A+987-6+5-43-(-2+1))$
8627	14719	$12-(-3456+7*-89A+B)$	$-B-(A9-8765)-(-43-2+1)$
8628	14720	$-12+3+45+6-(-7-89)*AB$	$-B-(A9-8765+43-2*1)$
8629	14721	$123-4+567+89*AB$	$-BA-9+8765+4*-3-21$
862A	14722	$(1+2+(3+4)^5+6)*7/8+9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9-8765)-(-43+2+1)$
862B	14723	$1-2-345+6*7+89AB$	$BA9+8+7654+3-21$
8630	14724	$-1-(2-3456-7*89A)+B$	$-BA9-(-8765+43-(-2+1))$
8631	14725	$-1+2-345+6*7+89AB$	$-BA-9-(-8765-4)-32+1$
8632	14726	$-1-2-(34-567-89A*B)$	$-B-(A9-8765)-(-4+32)-1$
8633	14727	$1+2-345-6*7+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765-43+2*1$
8634	14728	$1-2-34+567-89A*-B$	$-B-(A9-8765)-(-4+32-1)$
8635	14729	$123+4+567+89*AB$	$BA-(-9+8+7)-(6*54*32-1)$
8636	14730	$-1*2*(-345-6)*(-78+9A-B)$	$BA9-8+7654*(3-2)+1$
8637	14731	$1-(-2+3)-(-45-6)-(-7-89)*AB$	$BA9-8+7654-(-3-(-2+1))$
8638	14732	$1+2-(34-567)+89A*B$	$BA9-8+7654+3*(2-1)$
8639	14733	$1+((-2*-3)^4+5-6*7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA9-(8-7654-3)-(-2+1)$
863A	14734	$-1+((2+3)^4-(5+6))*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA9-8+7654+3*2-1$
863B	14735	$-12+3+4*567+89*A*-B$	$BA9-8+7654-3*2*1$
8640	14736	$12+3-(-45+6)-(-7-89)*AB$	$BA9+8+7654+3*(-2-1)$
8641	14737	$-1-23-4+567+89A*B$	$-B-A9+8765-4-3-21$
8642	14738	$12-345+6*7+89AB$	$B-A*(-987-65)-(-4+32-1)$
8643	14739	$-12-345-(6+7-89AB)$	$B-A9-(-8765+43+2-1)$
8644	14740	$-1-2-3+4*567+89*A*-B$	$B*A*(9-(-8-7-65+4-32+1))$
8645	14741	$12+3456+7*89A+B$	$BA9-(-8-7654+3)-(-2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8646	14742	$1 - (-2+3-4-56+(7+89))^* - AB$	$-BA+9 - (-8765-4)+32^* - 1$
8647	14743	$12-34+567-89A^* - B$	$B-A+8765-43+2+1$
8648	14744	$-1+2^* - 3^*4+567+89A^*B$	$BA9 - (-8-7654) - (3-2^*1)$
8649	14745	$-1-23 - (-4-567) - 89A^* - B$	$BA9+8+7654+3-2-1$
864A	14746	$1^*(2-3)^* - (-4^*567+89^* - A^*B)$	$BA9+8+7654+3-2^*1$
864B	14747	$1-23+4+567-89A^* - B$	$BA9 - (-8-7654) - (-3+2-1)$
8650	14748	$-12-3-4 - (-567+89A^* - B)$	$-BA-9 - (-8765+4+3^* - 2^* - 1)$
8651	14749	$-12+3^*456^*7+89A+B$	$B-A9 - (-8765+4+32)^*1$
8652	14750	$-1+2 - (34+56^*7)+89AB$	$BA9-8-765^* - 4^*3+21$
8653	14751	$-12-345+6-7+89AB$	$BA9+8+7654+3+2+1$
8654	14752	$-1-2-3^*4^* - 56-7-89A^* - B$	$-BA - (-9-8765) - (-4 - (-3-21))$
8655	14753	$-12-345-6 - (-7-89AB)$	$B-A98^* - 7+65^*(43 - (2-1))$
8656	14754	$-1+2-345-6 - (7-89AB)$	$-BA-9+8765-4+3-2-1$
8657	14755	$-123-45^*6-7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765 - (4-3) - 2^*1$
8658	14756	$1 - (-2+345+6) - 7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765+4-3^*2^*1$
8659	14757	$12-3+4^*567-89^*A^* - B$	$BA9-8+7654+3+21$
865A	14758	$-12+3 - (4 + (-56-7-89A)^*B)$	$-BA-9+8765-4+3+2-1$
865B	14759	$1-23-4+56^* - 7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765-4+3+2^*1$
8660	14760	$-1^*234^*5^*(6+78-9A+B)$	$-BA-9+8765-4+3+2+1$
8661	14761	$-1-2 - (3^* - 456 + (-7+89))^* - AB$	$-B-A9+8765-4-3-2+1$
8662	14762	$-1-2 - (345 - (6-7) - 89AB)$	$-BA-9+8765+4+3-2-1$
8663	14763	$12-34-56^*7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765 - (-4-3)+2^* - 1$
8664	14764	$1-2-345+6-7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765+4+3 - (2-1)$
8665	14765	$-12 - (345-6-7)+89AB$	$B - (A9-8765) - 4 - (-3+21)$
8666	14766	$1+2+3^* - 4^* - (-5-67)+89^*AB$	$-BA-9+8765+4+3+2-1$
8667	14767	$12-345-6-7+89AB$	$BA9 - (-8-7654+3-21)$
8668	14768	$-1+2 - (345 - (-6+7+89AB))$	$BA^*(98-76)^*(5-4)^*(3+2-1)$
8669	14769	$-123+45^* - 6+7+89AB$	$B-A^* - 987 - (6-543) - (-2-1)$
866A	14770	$-12^* - (-3+4)^*5^* - (-67+8-9-AB)$	$-BA+9+8765 - (4+3)+2-1$
866B	14771	$1+2+3-4+567-89A^* - B$	$B-A+9+8765+4^* - (-32+1)$
8670	14772	$-1+23-4^* - 567-89^* - A^*B$	$-BA+9+8765 - (4-3) - 2-1$
8671	14773	$123-456-7+89AB$	$-B-A9 - (-8765-4) - (3-2)+1$
8672	14774	$-12+3 - (4+56^*7)+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765-4+3-2+1$
8673	14775	$-12+3-45 - (67+89A)^* - B$	$-BA+9+8765 - (-4-3^* - 2-1)$
8674	14776	$-12-3+4-56^*7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765-4-3+21$
8675	14777	$12-3^*456^* - 7 - (-89A-B)$	$-B - (A9-8765-4 - (3 - (-2+1)))$
8676	14778	$1-2-345+6+7+89AB$	$B - (A9-8765)+4^*3-21$
8677	14779	$12-345 - (-6+7-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8765+4+3+2+1$
8678	14780	$12-345^* - (-6+7)+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765+4^* - (-3+2)^* - 1$
8679	14781	$1+234-567+89AB$	$-BA+9 - (-8765-4 - (-3+2)^* - 1)$
867A	14782	$1+2-345+6+7+89AB$	$BA9 - (-8-7654-32) - 1$
867B	14783	$-1+2-3-4-56^*7+89AB$	$BA9 - (-8-7654-32^*1)$
8680	14784	$12-3+4+567+89A^*B$	$-B^* - (-A-987-6-5+43+21)$
8681	14785	$-1-2+3-4-56^*7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765-4-3+2-1$
8682	14786	$-1+2^* - 3+4 - (-56^* - 7-89AB)$	$-BA - (-9-8765+4^* - 3-2^* - 1)$
8683	14787	$123 - (456-7)+89AB$	$-BA - (-9-8765)+4^*3 - (2-1)$
8684	14788	$-1-2+3^* - 4 - (5^*6+78-9)^* - AB$	$B-A9+8765+4+3^* - 2-1$
8685	14789	$-1+2+3-4-56^*7+89AB$	$B - (A9-8765-4+3+2+1)$
8686	14790	$123+456+7+89A^*B$	$-BA-9+8765+4+3+21$
8687	14791	$-1 - (-23+4)+567-89A^* - B$	$B - (A9-8765-4) - (3+2-1)$
8688	14792	$1-2+3456-7^* - (-89A-B)$	$B-A9+8765 - (4 - (3-2^* - 1))$
8689	14793	$12-345+6+7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765 - (-4+3-2+1)$
868A	14794	$-12-345-6^* - 7+89AB$	$-BA - (-9-8765+4+3-21)$
868B	14795	$-12+34+567+89A^*B$	$-B-A9+8765+43-21$
8690	14796	$12-3-4+56^* - 7+89AB$	$-B-A - (-9-8765)+43^* - 2+1$
8691	14797	$-1+2+3-456-7^* - 89^*(A+B)$	$B-A9+8765+4+3-2+1$
8692	14798	$12^* - (-3+45+6-789)^*(A-B)$	$BA98-76^*54-3-2-1$
8693	14799	$-1+23 - (-4-567) - 89A^* - B$	$-BA - (9-8765 - (4+32)+1)$
8694	14800	$-1^* - (-23 - (-4 - (-567-89A^*B)))$	$-BA - (9-8765-4) - 32^* - 1$
8695	14801	$-1 - (-2345+6) - 78^* - 9A+B$	$-B - (A9-8765-4 - (3+21))$
8696	14802	$-12-34-5^*67+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765 - (-43+21)$
8697	14803	$1-2+(-3+(-4-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9+8765-43-21$
8698	14804	$(1+2^*3)^*((4+5-6)^7-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA9-8+7654-3^*-21$
8699	14805	$-1-2-345-6^* - 7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765-4^* - 3-2^* - 1$
869A	14806	$-12+3 - (4-56)^* - 7+89AB$	$-BA-9+8765 - (-43+2+1)$
869B	14807	$12+3456+7^*(89A+B)$	$-BA-9+8765+43-2^*1$
86A0	14808	$-12+3-4^*5+(67+89A)^*B$	$-BA - (9-8765)+43 - (2-1)$
86A1	14809	$-1 - (-2+345) - 6^* - 7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765-4-3+21$
86A2	14810	$12 - (-3-4-56^* - 7-89AB)$	$BA98+76^* - 54+3^* - 2^* - 1$
86A3	14811	$-1 - (-23+4-56^* - 7-89AB)$	$-B - (A9-8765-4+32^* - 1)$
86A4	14812	$1-23+4-5+(-67-89A)^* - B$	$-B-A9+8765+4 - (-32-1)$
86A5	14813	$1 - (-23+4+56^*7)+89AB$	$-B-A^* - 987+6^*(54+3^*21)$
86A6	14814	$1+23-45 - (-67-89A)^*B$	$-B+A9+87-6^* - 54^*32+1$
86A7	14815	$-12+34-56^*7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765-4+3+21$
86A8	14816	$(-1-2/3+(-4-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B-A+9^* - 87^* - 6 - (-5432+1)$
86A9	14817	$-1+2-34-5^*67+89AB$	$-B-A^*9 - (8765+4+3+2)^* - 1$
86AA	14818	$-1-23^* - (-456 - (7-89))^*+AB$	$-B-A9+8765 - (-43+2^*1)$
86AB	14819	$1+2-34-5^*67+89AB$	$-B-A9+8765+43-2+1$
86B0	14820	$1^* - (-2+34)^* - (-5-67^*(89-A^*B))$	$-B-A9+8765-43^*(- 2+1)$
86B1	14821	$1+23 - (-4+56^*7)+89AB$	$-B-A9+8765 - (-43-2) - 1$
86B2	14822	$12-345-6^* - 7+89AB$	$-B - (A9-8765-43)+2^*1$
86B3	14823	$-123+4^* - 56+7+89AB$	$-B+A-9+8765-43-21$
86B4	14824	$-1-23-4+5^* - 67+89AB$	$B - (A9-8765) - (4-32+1)$
86B5	14825	$1^* - 2^*3+(-4-5^*-6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9 - (-8765-43+2^*1)$
86B6	14826	$-1-2+34+56^* - 7+89AB$	$-B-A-9+8765-43+2^* - 1$
86B7	14827	$1^2+(-3+(-4-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A+B$	$-B - (A+9-8765+43 - (-2+1))$
86B8	14828	$1-2+34-56^*7+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765 - (-43 - (2-1))$
86B9	14829	$1+2+(-3+(-4-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A+B$	$-B-A-9 - (-8765+43-2+1)$
86BA	14830	$12-34-5^*67+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765 - (-43 - (2+1))$
86BB	14831	$-12 - (345 - (67+89AB))$	$-B-A - (9 - (8765-43) - (2+1))$
8700	14832	$-1 - (23-4-5^*-67-89AB)$	$B - (A9-8765) - (-4-32+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8701	14833	$1 - (2^*3)^4 + 5^6 + 7^*8^*9 + A - B$	$B - A + 8765 + 4 - 32^* - 1$
8702	14834	$1 - 23 + 4 - (5^*67 - 89AB)$	$-BA - 9 + 8765 + 43 + 21$
8703	14835	$-12 - 3 - (4 - 5^* - 67 - 89AB)$	$B + A + 87 + 6^* - 54^* - 32^* + 1$
8704	14836	$-1 - (-2 + 3) - (-4 - (-5 - (67 + 89A))^* - B)$	$-B - A - (9 - (8765 - 4)) - (32 + 1)$
8705	14837	$-12 + 3 - (-4 - 5) - (67 + 89A)^* - B$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 - 4 + 32^* - 1$
8706	14838	$-1 - (234 + 5 - (-67 + 89AB))$	$-B - A - (9 - 8765) - (4 + 32) + 1$
8707	14839	$-1^*(234 - (-5 - 67 + 89AB))$	$B - (A9 - 8765) + 43 - 2 - 1$
8708	14840	$1 - 234 - 5 - (67 - 89AB)$	$-B - A9 + 8765 - 4 + 3^*21$
8709	14841	$-12 + 3 - 4 + 5^* - 67 + 89AB$	$B - A9 + 8765 + 43 - 2 + 1$
870A	14842	$-1 - 2 - (345 - 67 - 89AB)$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 - (-4^* - 3 + 21)$
870B	14843	$1^* - 2 - 345 + 67 + 89AB$	$B - A + 9 + 8765 - (43 + 21)$
8710	14844	$1 - 2 - 345 - (-67 - 89AB)$	$B - (A9 - 8765) - (-43 - 2^*1)$
8711	14845	$-1 - 23^* - 4 + 56 + (7 + 89)^*AB$	$-B - A + 9 - 8^* - 76^*5^*4 + 321$
8712	14846	$-1 - (-2 + 345 - 67 - 89AB)$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 + 4 - 32 + 1$
8713	14847	$1^*2 - 345 - (-67 - 89AB)$	$B - A - 9 + 8765 - 43 - 2 - 1$
8714	14848	$-1 - 234 + 5 - (67 - 89AB)$	$B - A - 9 + 8765 + (43 + 2)^* - 1$
8715	14849	$-1 - (234 + 56) - (7 - 89AB)$	$-B + A^*(987 + 6 + 5 - (-43 - 21))$
8716	14850	$-1 - 23 - 456^* - 7 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$B - (-A + 9) - (-8765 - 4) - 3^*21$
8717	14851	$1 - 234 - 56 - 7 + 89AB$	$B - A - 9 + 8765 - (43 - (2 - 1))$
8718	14852	$1 - 23 - 456^* - 7 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8765 + 43 + 21$
8719	14853	$-1 - 2 + 3456 - 7^*(8 + 9A^* - B)$	$B + A - 9^*(87 + 65 + 4^* - 321)$
871A	14854	$1 + 2^* - 3 + 4^*5 - (-67 - 89A)^*B$	$-B - A - (-9 - 8765 + 4) - (-32 + 1)$
871B	14855	$1 - 2^* - 3^* - 45 - (67 - 89AB)$	$-B - (A - 9) + 8765 - (4 - 32^* - 1)$
8720	14856	$-1 + 2 - (-3 + 4) - (-5^* - 67 - 89AB)$	$B + A^* - 9 + 8765 + 43 - 21$
8721	14857	$12 + 34 - (5 - 6 - 7 - 89)^*AB$	$-B - A9 + 8765 + 4^*(- 3 + 21)$
8722	14858	$-1 + 2 - (3 - 4) - (-5^* - 67 - 89AB)$	$B - A - 9 + 8765 - 4 - (32 + 1)$
8723	14859	$12 - 345 + 67 + 89AB$	$-BA - (9 - 8765 + 43^* - 2 + 1)$
8724	14860	$123 + 4 + (-5 - 6)^*(78 - 9AB)$	$B + A - (-9 - 8765) - 4 + 3^* - 21$
8725	14861	$-12 - 3 - (-456^*7 + 8^*9A^* - B)$	$-BA - 9 + 8765 + 43^*2 + 1$
8726	14862	$1 + 2^*345 - 67 - 89A^* - B$	$-B - A + 9 + 8765 - (-4 + 32 + 1)$
8727	14863	$-1 - 234 - 56 + 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - (-9 - 8765) - (43 + 21)$
8728	14864	$1^* - 234 - 56 + 7 + 89AB$	$-B + A - (9 - (8765 + 4)) - (-32 + 1)$
8729	14865	$1 - 234 - 56 + 7 + 89AB$	$-B + A + 9 + 8^* - 76^*5^* - 4 + 321$
872A	14866	$1 + 2 - (-3 - 4 - 5^* - 67) + 89AB$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 + 4 - 32 + 1$
872B	14867	$1 - 2 - 3^* - 4 - 5^*67 + 89AB$	$B - A9 + 8765 + 43 + 21$
8730	14868	$-1^* - 2^*(3 + 4)^*(- 5^*6 + 789 - A - B)$	$B - (-A + 9) - (-8765 + 43) - 2^*1$
8731	14869	$1 + 2^*(- 345 + 6 - 7 - 8^* - 9^* - A^* - B)$	$B - A + 9 + 8765 - 43 + 2 - 1$
8732	14870	$1 + 2^*34 + 56^* - 7 + 89AB$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 - 2^*1$
8733	14871	$12 - 3 + 4 + 5^* - 67 + 89AB$	$B - (-A + 9) - (-8765 + 43 - 2 + 1)$
8734	14872	$-1^*(- 2 - 3 - (4 + 56) - (7 + 89A))^*B$	$B + A - 9 + 8765 - (43 + 2^* - 1)$
8735	14873	$((1 + 2)^3 - 4^5 + 6)^*(- 7 - 8) + 9 + A - B$	$-B + A - 9 + 8765 - 43 + 21$
8736	14874	$1^* - 2^*(- 3 - (-4 - 56))^*(- 7 - (89 + A - B))$	$B + A9 - 8 + 7^* - 6^*(5 + 4)^*(- 32 - 1)$
8737	14875	$123 + 4 + 5^*(6 + 78)^*(9 + A + B)$	$B - (A + 9 - 8765 + 43 - 21)$
8738	14876	$-1^*(234 - (-5 - 6^*7) - 89AB)$	$-B + A9 + 8765 + 4^* - 32 + 1$
8739	14877	$1 - (234 + 5 + 6^*7 - 89AB)$	$B - A - 9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 - 21$
873A	14878	$1 - 23^* - 4 - (-567 + 89A^* - B)$	$B - (A - (9 + 8765 - 4)) - (-32 + 1))$
873B	14879	$-1 + 2^* - 3^*4^*(567 + 8 - 9AB)$	$BA98 + 76^* - 54 + 3^*21$
8740	14880	$1234 - 56 + 78^*(9 + AB)$	$-B + A + 9 - (-8765 + 4^*3) - 21$
8741	14881	$-1 + 234 - (-567 + 89^* - AB)$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 + 2 - 1$
8742	14882	$-12 + 34 - 5^*67 + 89AB$	$-B - (-A - 9 - 8765 - 4 - (-32 - 1))$
8743	14883	$1234 - 5 - 6 - (-7 + 89)^* - AB$	$B^*(A + 9 - 8)^*(- 7 + 65 + 43 + 2^*1)$
8744	14884	$-12 - 3^* - 4^* - 5^*6 - (-7 - 89AB)$	$B - A^* - 98^*7 - (6 + 5)^* - 432 - 1$
8745	14885	$-1 - 234 - 5^*6 - 7 + 89AB$	$B - (-A - 9) - (-8765 + 43) - (2 + 1)$
8746	14886	$1 - (-2 + 3^*(4 - 5))^* - 6^* - 78^*9 + A + B)$	$-B + A - 9 + 8765 + 4^*3 - 21$
8747	14887	$1 - 234 + 5^*6 - 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - (-9 - 8765) - (43 + 2 - 1)$
8748	14888	$1 - (-23 - 4 - 5^* - 67 - 89AB)$	$-BA + 9 + 8765 + 4^*(3 + 21)$
8749	14889	$(-1 + 2^3 - 3^*4 + 5^*6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9 + A + B$	$BA - 9 - (-8765 - 4^* - 32 + 1)$
874A	14890	$123 - (-45 + 6 - (-7 - 89)^* - AB)$	$BA - 9 + 8765 - 4^* - 32^* - 1$
874B	14891	$1 + 2^*3^*(- 45 - 6) - 7 + 89AB$	$-B + A - (9 - 8765 + 43 - 21)$
8750	14892	$-1 - 2^*(- 3 / - 4 - 5 - 6) / - 7^*(8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$-B - A - (9 - (8765 - 4^* - 3)) - (-2 + 1)$
8751	14893	$1 + 23^*4 + (5 - 67 - 89A)^* - B$	$B - (A - 9 - 8765 + 43 - 21)$
8752	14894	$-1 + 2345 + 6 + 78^*(9 + A^*B)$	$-B - A + 9 + 8765^*(4 - 3) - (2 + 1)$
8753	14895	$1 + (-2 + 3 + 4)^*(- 5 - 6^* - 7^*8)^*9 + A - B$	$B - (-A + 9 - 8765 + 43 - 21)$
8754	14896	$-1^* - 2^*(- 345 + 6 + 7 + 8^*9 + A^*B)$	$-B + A987 - 65^*(43 - 2) + 1$
8755	14897	$12 - 3^*(4 + 567^* - 8 + 9AB)$	$-B + A - 9 - (-8765 - 4) + 3^*2^* - 1$
8756	14898	$-1 - 2 + 3^*456^*7 - 8 + 9AB$	$B + A9 + 8765 - 4^*32 + 1$
8757	14899	$1 + 2 + 34 - 5^*67 + 89AB$	$-B - A^*(- 987 - 6 - 54 + 3 - 21)$
8758	14900	$1^* - 234 - 5^*6 + 7 + 89AB$	$B - (-A + 9 - 8765 + 4^*(3 + 2)) - 1$
8759	14901	$-1^*2 - 3^*(- 4 - 5^*(6 + 7))^*8^*9 + A - B$	$-B - (-A + 9 - 8765 - (-4 + 3^* - 2^* - 1))$
875A	14902	$12 + 3 + 4^*5 - 56^*7^* - 8 - (9^* - A - B)$	$-B - (-A + 9 - 8765) + 4 - (3 + 2^* - 1)$
875B	14903	$12 - 3 + 45 - (67 + 89A)^* - B$	$-B - A98 + 76^*(- 54 + 3^*)^*(- 2 - 1)$
8760	14904	$-1 - 234 - (5 + 6) - (7 - 89AB)$	$BA + 9 + 8765 + 4^*(- 32 - 1)$
8761	14905	$1234 + 5 - (-6 - (-7 + 89)^*AB)$	$-B - (A + 9 - 8765 - 4 + 3 - 21)$
8762	14906	$1 + 23 - 456^* - 7 - 8^* - 9A^*B$	$-B - (A - 9 - 8765 - 4) - (-3 + 2^* - 1)$
8763	14907	$1^*2 - 3^*(- 4 - 5^*(6 + 7))^*8^*9 - (A - B)$	$B + A^*987 + 654 + 3 - 21$
8764	14908	$1 + 23 + 4^*5^* - 6^*(7 - (-8 + 9)^*AB)$	$BA + 9 + 8765 + 4^* - 32^*1$
8765	14909	$-12 - 3 - 45^*6 - 7 + 89AB$	$B - A + 9 + 8765 - (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)$
8766	14910	$12 + 34 - 5^*67 + 89AB$	$BA^*(98 - 76^* - 5 - 4 - 321)$
8767	14911	$-1 + (2 - (3^*4 - 5)^6) / (-7 - 8 / 9) + A - B$	$B - A - (9 - 8765) + 4 - (-3 - 2 - 1)$
8768	14912	$-1 - 23 + 45^* - 6 + 7 + 89AB$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 - 4 + 32 - 1$
8769	14913	$1 - (2 - (3^*4 - 5)^6) / (7 + 8 / 9) + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
876A	14914	$-1 - 2 - 3^* - 456^*7 - (-8 - 9AB)$	$B - (A - 9 - 8765) - (4 + 3) + 2^*1$
876B	14915	$1^* - 234 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89AB$	$B - A - (-9 - 8765 + 4 + 3 - 2) + 1$
8770	14916	$-1 - 234 - 5 + 6 - 7 + 89AB$	$-B^*(- A + 9 + 8 - (-76 + 543)^*2 - 1)$
8771	14917	$123 - 4^* - 567 - 89^* - A^*B$	$B - (A - 9) - (-8765 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)$
8772	14918	$-1 + 2 + 3^*456^*7 + 8 + 9AB$	$B - (-A987 + 65^*(43 - 2) - 1)$
8773	14919	$1 + 23^*4^* - 5 - (-6 - 7 - 89)^*AB$	$B + A - 9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)$
8774	14920	$1 - 234 - 5 - 6 + 7 + 89AB$	$-B - (A9 - 8765) - (-4^*32 + 1)$
8775	14921	$-1^*(2 + 3 + 45^*6 - (-7 + 89AB))$	$-B - A + 9 - (-8765 + 4 - 3 - 21)$
8776	14922	$1 - 2^* - 3^*(4 - 56 + 7) + 89AB$	$-B - A - 9 + 8765 + 4 + 32 + 1$
8777	14923	$1 - (2 + 3)^4 + 5^6 - 7 - 8^*9 - (A - B)$	$B - A + 9 + 8765 + 4 + 3 - 2 - 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8778	14924	$12^*(34-56+789-A-B)$	$B-A+9+8765+4-(-3+2^*1)$
8779	14925	$1234-5-(6+78^*(-9-AB))$	$-B-(-A+9)-(-8765-4)-(3-21)$
877A	14926	$-1-234+5-(-6+7-89AB)$	$B+A-9+8765-(-4-3-2^*-1)$
877B	14927	$-1-234+5^*(-6+7)+89AB$	$-B-(A-(-9+8765))-4(3-2)+1$
8780	14928	$-1-234-(-5+6)-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-A-(9-(8765+43+2^*-1))$
8781	14929	$-12-(-3+45^*6)-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-A+9+8765+4+3+21$
8782	14930	$-1-234-5-(-6-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9+8765-(-4-(3-2^*-1))$
8783	14931	$-1-23-(-4^*(-56-7)-89AB)$	$B-(-A+9)-(-8765-4)+3^*-2^*-1$
8784	14932	$1+2+3+45^*-6-7+89AB$	$-B-A-(-9-8765)-4(3-2-1)$
8785	14933	$-1-(2+3)^{A+5}6-7^*8-9+A-B$	$-BA98-7^*(6+5)^*(-4-321)$
8786	14934	$-1^*-2^*(-34+56-78+9)^*-AB$	$B-(A+9-(8765-4))+32-1$
8787	14935	$-1-2^*-34-5^*67+89AB$	$B+A^*987-(-654-3-(2+1))$
8788	14936	$123-(4-567)-89A^*-B$	$B-A-9+8765-4(3-2-1)$
8789	14937	$-1+2^*(345+6-7)-89A^*-B$	$B+A+9+8765+4+3^*2^*-1$
878A	14938	$12^*(345-6-7^*(-89-(-A-B)))$	$B+A+9+8765+4-3-2^*1$
878B	14939	$((1-2^A3)^{A+5})^*6-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A-(9+8765))-4-(-3-(2-1))$
8790	14940	$-1-234+5+6+7+89AB$	$-B-(A-9876+5-4^*-321)$
8791	14941	$-1-23^*-4-5+(-67-89A)^*-B$	$-B+A-9+8765-(-4+32^*-1)$
8792	14942	$1-234+5+6+7+89AB$	$-B+A-(9-8765)-(-4-(32+1))$
8793	14943	$1+23+4^*(-5-67)+89AB$	$-B-(-A-9)+8765+43-21$
8794	14944	$123+4+567-89A^*-B$	$B-A-(9-8765-4-(32+1))$
8795	14945	$-12-34+5+6^*-7^*(8+9)^*(-A-B)$	$B+A-9+8765-4+3+21$
8796	14946	$1+2+3-45^*6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8765-(-43^*-2+1)$
8797	14947	$12-3-4^*-56+7+89)^*AB$	$-B+A^*9+8765-4-32+1$
8798	14948	$-123-(45-(-67+89AB))$	$-B+A9-(-8765-(-4-3^*21))$
8799	14949	$1-23^*(-45-6)+789A-B$	$-B+A-9+8765-(-43+2-1)$
879A	14950	$-1+23-(-4^*-56^*7^*-8-9)+AB$	$-B-A+9876+5-4^*321$
879B	14951	$1+2+34^*-5^*-6-7+89^*AB$	$-B-(-A9-8765)-4(3+21)$
87A0	14952	$12^*3^*4^*(-56-(-7-8-9)+AB)$	$-B+A+9+8765-4+32+1$
87A1	14953	$-123+4^*-5^*6-7+89AB$	$B-(A+9-(8765+43-(-2+1)))$
87A2	14954	$1-23-4^*56-7+89AB$	$B-A-(-9-8765+4-(32+1))$
87A3	14955	$1-2-345-(-6+7^*89^*(-A-B))$	$-B-A-9-(-8765-43-21)$
87A4	14956	$123-4-56^*7+89AB$	$B+A-9-(-8765+4)+32+1$
87A5	14957	$12+3+45^*-6-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A^*9+8765-43-2^*1$
87A6	14958	$1-23^*(-456+78)-(-9A+B)$	$-B-(-A-9)+8765+4-(-32+1)$
87A7	14959	$-1-234-5+6^*7+89AB$	$B+A-9-(-8765-43^*-2)+1$
87A8	14960	$-12345-6^*7^*8^*-9A-B$	$-B+A+9+8765+4-(-32-1)$
87A9	14961	$1-(234-5^*6-(7+89AB))$	$B+A+9+8765-4^*(-3+21)$
87AA	14962	$1+2^*3^*-4^*-56+789A+B$	$B+A-9+8765+4+32-1$
87AB	14963	$-1-23^*-4-5^*6+7+89AB$	$-B+A^*9+8765^*(4-3)-21$
87B0	14964	$123+4+56^*-7+89AB$	$B+A-9+8765+4+32+1$
87B1	14965	$1+(-2+3-4)^5(-6-7)/8)^*9-(A+B)$	$B+A-(-9-8765-(43-21))$
87B2	14966	$-12^*(3+4^*5+6+7+8+9)^*-AB$	$B-A-9+8765-43-21$
87B3	14967	$1^*23-45^*6+7+89AB$	$-B-(-A-9)-(-8765-43+2-1)$
87B4	14968	$1-23-4^*56-(-7-89AB)$	$B-A+9-(8765+43-2)^*-1$
87B5	14969	$-1-(234-5)+6^*7+89AB$	$B-A+9+8765+43-2+1$
87B6	14970	$12-345+6+7^*89^*(A+B)$	$-B+A+9876+5+4^*-321$
87B7	14971	$1+23^*(45+6)+789A+B$	$-B+A+9-(-8765-43-2-1)$
87B8	14972	$12-(-3+4^*(-5+67)-89AB)$	$B-A-(-9-8765)-4^*(-3+21)$
87B9	14973	$-1^*(-2+345)^*(-6-7-8-9+A-B)$	$B-(-A+9-8765)-(-43-2+1)$
87BA	14974	$-1-2-3+4^*-56-7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765+43+2^*1)$
87BB	14975	$1+2+34^*-5-6+7+89AB$	$-B-(-A+9)-(-8765-(43+21))$
8800	14976	$1-(2+3-4^*-56)-7+89AB$	$B+A987-6^*(5+432^*1)$
8801	14977	$-12-3+4^*-56+7+89AB$	$B-A-9+8765+43+21$
8802	14978	$1+2+(3+45+67-8)^*9A-B$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*(-7+6)^*-5^*(4+32)^*1$
8803	14979	$-12+3+45^*6-(-7-89)^*AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765+43-(2+1))$
8804	14980	$12^*(3-(45-6-(789-A)-B))$	$B-A-9-(-8765-(4+3^*21))$
8805	14981	$-123+4^*-5-(-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9-(-8765-4)+32^*1$
8806	14982	$1-2^*-34^*(-5^*-6^*7-8)+9^*-AB$	$B+A^*-9+8765+4^*-32^*-1$
8807	14983	$1-234+56-7+89AB$	$-B-A^*9+8765-(-4+3)^*-21$
8808	14984	$(-1-2-3^*4-5^*-6^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8765-(43+21)$
8809	14985	$-123-45+6^*-7+89AB$	$-B+A9+8765-(-4+32^*1)$
880A	14986	$12-34^*5-(-67-89AB)$	$-B+A9-(-8765-(-4-32)))+1$
880B	14987	$1+23+4^*(-56-7)+89AB$	$-B+A+9+8^*-76^*(5-(4-(3-21)))$
8810	14988	$-1+234^*5-6+789A-B$	$B+A+9+8765+43-2^*1$
8811	14989	$1-23-(4^*(56-7)-89AB)$	$B-A-9+8765-43+2^*-1$
8812	14990	$1+234^*5-6-(-789A+B)$	$B-A-9+8765-(43+2-1)$
8813	14991	$12-3+4^*-56-7+89AB$	$B+A-(-9-8765-43-2+1)$
8814	14992	$-123-4-(5+67)+89AB$	$B+A-(-9876-5-4^*-321)$
8815	14993	$1-2+3-4^*5^*(6+7)+89AB$	$-B+A9+8765-(-4+32^*1)$
8816	14994	$-1-23^*(4+5)-6-7+89AB$	$-B+A9+8765+4-32+1$
8817	14995	$-1-(234-(56+7))+89AB$	$B-A+9+8765+43+21$
8818	14996	$-1-234-5-(-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8765+(43+2)^*-1$
8819	14997	$1-(234-56-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9+8765-43-2+1$
881A	14998	$1-234-(-5-67)+89AB$	$-B-A-(-9-8765-(43^*2-1))$
881B	14999	$-1+2-3^*-45-(-67-89A)^*B$	$B-A+9+8765-4-32-1$
8820	15000	$-123+4-5-6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8765-43+2^*1$
8821	15001	$12+3^*-4+5-6^*-7^*(8+9)^*(A+B)$	$B-A-9+8765-4(3+2)+1$
8822	15002	$-123-(4-5+67)+89AB$	$B-(A+9)-(-8765-43^*2+1)$
8823	15003	$-123-4-56-(7-89AB)$	$-B+A+9+8765+4-(3+21)$
8824	15004	$-1+2^*-3^*(4+5^*6+7)+89AB$	$-B+A+9^*8^*7^*6^*5-(-43+21)$
8825	15005	$12-3+4^*-56+7+89AB$	$B-A^*-9+8765-4-3+2^*1$
8826	15006	$-1-234+5+6+7+89AB$	$B-A-(-9-8765)-43-(2+1)$
8827	15007	$1^*-234-(-5-67-89AB)$	$B-A-9+8765+4-32-1$
8828	15008	$12^*(-34-(56-7+8-9^*AB))$	$B+A+9+8765-43-2+1$
8829	15009	$-1-2+3^*-45^*(-67-8)-9^*-AB$	$-B+A+9+8765+4+3-21$
882A	15010	$-123+4+5-6+7+89AB$	$B-A-(-9-8765)-(43-2)-1$
882B	15011	$-123-(-4+5+6+7)+89AB$	$B-A-(-9-8765-(-43-2^*-1))$
8830	15012	$-1-234^*5-(6+7)^*(-89A-B)$	$B+A+9+8765-4^*3-21$
8831	15013	$-1+2-(-3^*45^*(6+7+8)-9^*AB)$	$B+A+9^*8^*7^*6^*5-4^A3^*2^*1$
8832	15014	$-123-45-6-(7-89AB)$	$B-(-A9-8765)-(-4+32+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8833	15015	$12-34+5*6*-7+89AB$	$B*(-A-9-8+7+654+321)$
8834	15016	$1+2-3*45-67+89AB$	$B+A9-(-8765-4+32)+1$
8835	15017	$-123-4-56+7+89AB$	$B-(-A9-8765)-(4+3)-21$
8836	15018	$-1+2*345+67+89A*B$	$BA-9+8765+4-(3+21)$
8837	15019	$123+4+5-(67+89A)*-B$	$BA+9+8765-4-(32-1)$
8838	15020	$-12-3*(4+56)-(7-89AB)$	$-B-(-A-(9+8765)-43*2)+1$
8839	15021	$-123+4*5-67+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765-(-4-3+2-1))$
883A	15022	$-1-234*5-(-6-789A-B)$	$-B+A9+876*(5+4-3)*(-2-1)$
883B	15023	$123-4+5*-67+89AB$	$B+A9+8765-(4-3+21)$
8840	15024	$1*(-23+4+5+6)*(7-89A+B)$	$BA-9+8765+4+3-21$
8841	15025	$-123+4-(56-7)+89AB$	$-B+A9+8765-4+3-2+1$
8842	15026	$-123-45+6-7+89AB$	$-B+A98+7654+321$
8843	15027	$12-3*45-67+89AB$	$BA+9+8765+4-32+1$
8844	15028	$-123-45-6+7+89AB$	$-B-(-A9-8765)-(4-3)-2*-1$
8845	15029	$-123-(4+5+6*7-89AB)$	$-B+A9+8765-4+3+2+1$
8846	15030	$-12-3*(-4-5)*6*78-(-9-AB)$	$-B+A9+8765+4-3-2*-1$
8847	15031	$123+4-5*67+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765-4)+3-(2+1)$
8848	15032	$1-2*(-3-4*5*-6*7+8)*9-(A-B)$	$BA-9+8765-4-3-2-1$
8849	15033	$1-2-3-4-5*6*7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765-(4+3-2+1))$
884A	15034	$-1+(-2/(-3*-4)+5*6)*(-7*-8*9)+A-B$	$BA+9+8765-43+21$
884B	15035	$-1+2-(3+4-5*6*-7-89AB)$	$-B+A9+8765+4+3+2-1$
8850	15036	$-12-3*45-6*7+89AB$	$BA-(-9-8765-4)-(3+21)$
8851	15037	$-12-34*5-(6-7)*89AB$	$-B+A9+8765-(-4-3)+2+1$
8852	15038	$1-2-3^4+5^6-7*8*9+A-B$	$BA-9+8765-4+3-2-1$
8853	15039	$-1+2-34*5-6-7+89AB$	$-B+A9+8765-4*-3*(2-1)$
8854	15040	$-123-45-(-6-7-89AB)$	$BA-9+8765+4-3-2-1$
8855	15041	$1+2-3^4+5*6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA-98-76*5*(4-32)-1$
8856	15042	$1+2-3^4+5^6-7*8*9+A-B$	$BA-9+8765-(4-(3+2-1))$
8857	15043	$12+34+5*-6*-7*-8*-9-AB$	$B+A9+8765-4-3+2-1$
8858	15044	$-1-(2+3)^4+5^6+7+8+9+A+B$	$BA-9+8765-4-(-3-2-1)$
8859	15045	$-1*(234-56-7)*(8*9-AB)$	$B+A9-(-8765+4+3)-(-2-1)$
885A	15046	$-1+2*(-3+456+7)-89*-AB$	$B+A9+8765+4-3*2-1$
885B	15047	$1+2+3*(4-56-7)+89AB$	$BA-9+8765-(4+3*(-2-1))$
8860	15048	$1*-2*(-3-4+56+7)*(8+9-AB)$	$B-(-A9-87654)+321$
8861	15049	$123-456*7-8*9A*-B$	$B+A9+8765-4+3+2-1$
8862	15050	$12*(3+4-56+789+A+B)$	$-B-(-A9-8765+4*3*-2+1)$
8863	15051	$1*2+(-3+4-5*6*7)*8*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8765-4+3+21$
8864	15052	$1+2+(-3+4-5*6*7)*8*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8765+4*-3*-2+1$
8865	15053	$-12+3*(-45-6)-7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765-(43-21))$
8866	15054	$-123-(-45-(-67+89AB))$	$B+A9+8765-(-4-3+2*1)$
8867	15055	$1+2-(-34*-5-(-6+7))+89AB$	$BA+9-(-8765+4+3)-2*-1$
8868	15056	$12-3-(-4+5*-6*-7-89AB)$	$BA-(-9-8765)-4-(-3+2)-1$
8869	15057	$-1-2*(3456-789A+B)$	$B+A9+8765+4+3-(-2+1)$
886A	15058	$-1*2*(3456-789A+B)$	$B+A9+8765+4-3*-2-1$
886B	15059	$1-(2+3*-4*(5+6-(-789-AB)))$	$-B+A9+8765+4+3+21$
8870	15060	$1*2+(-3-(4-5*-6*-7*8))*9-(A-B)$	$BA-9+8765-4-3+21$
8871	15061	$1+2*(-3-45)-67+89AB$	$BA+9-(-8765+4-3*2+1)$
8872	15062	$123-4*56*7*-8+9A-B$	$-B-(-A9-8765+4)-(-32-1)$
8873	15063	$1-2-34*5+6+7+89AB$	$BA+9+8765-4+3*2+1$
8874	15064	$-123-4*(5+6-7)+89AB$	$BA+9-(-8765-4)-(-3+2+1)$
8875	15065	$12+3*(-456+7)*-8+9*(-A-B)$	$B-A9*-8*-7+6543*2*1$
8876	15066	$-1*-23*(456-78+9A-B)$	$BA-9+8765-4+3+21$
8877	15067	$12-3*-4-5*-6*-7+89AB$	$B+A9+8765-4-3+21$
8878	15068	$-123-4+5-6-7+89AB$	$BA-9+8765+43-21$
8879	15069	$-123-45-6*-7+89AB$	$B+A-9-(-8765+4*(-32+1))$
887A	15070	$1-2*(3456-789A)-B$	$-B+A9+8765-(-4-32-1)$
887B	15071	$-123-4+5*(6-7)+89AB$	$B-A+9+8765-4*-32*1$
8880	15072	$-123-4-(5-(-6+7+89AB))$	$B+A-9+8765+4*32-1$
8881	15073	$-123+4*5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A9+8765-(4-3-21)$
8882	15074	$1*-2*(3+4567-89AB)$	$BA-(9-8765-4-(3+21))$
8883	15075	$-1+2345-6-789*-A+B$	$B-(-A9-8765)-(-4+3-21)$
8884	15076	$-1-2-3*45-6-7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765-43)+2*-1$
8885	15077	$1+2345-6-789*-A+B$	$BA-9+8765-4+32+1$
8886	15078	$-123-(-4+5-6)-7+89AB$	$BA+9+8765-4-(3-21)$
8887	15079	$-123+4-(-5*(6-7)-89AB)$	$BA-9-(-8765+4*-3)+21$
8888	15080	$-123+4-(5+6-(7+89AB))$	$BA-9+8765-4*(3+2)*-1$
8889	15081	$-1*(-2-34-56+7-89A)*B$	$B+A9+8765+4+3+21$
888A	15082	$-123-(4-5)-6-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A*(987+6+5+4+32)+1$
888B	15083	$1-23*(-4-5)+(67+89A)*B$	$BA-(9-(8765+4))+32-1$
8890	15084	$-123-4-5+6+7+89AB$	$BA-(-9-(8765-4)-3-21)$
8891	15085	$-1+2*(3-(4567-89AB))$	$BA-9+8765+4+32+1$
8892	15086	$123-4*(5+67)+89AB$	$B+A+9+8765+4-3+21$
8893	15087	$-1+2345+6+789*A+B$	$B-(-A-9)+8765-4*(-32+1)$
8894	15088	$-123+4+5+6-7+89AB$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7+6)*(5-4^3/2)+1$
8895	15089	$1-(-2345-6)-789*-A+B$	$B-A+9+87+6*-54*(-32-1)$
8896	15090	$-123+4+5-(6-7-89AB)$	$B+A9-(-8765-4-32+1)$
8897	15091	$-1-23-45-(67-89AB)$	$B-(-A9-8765-4*-3*-21)$
8898	15092	$-123+4-5-(-6-7-89AB)$	$BA-9+8765+43-2+1$
8899	15093	$1-23-(45+67-89AB)$	$BA+9+8765-4+32-1$
889A	15094	$-123-(4-5-6-7-89AB)$	$BA-9-(-8765-43-(2-1))$
889B	15095	$123+4*-56*-7*8+9+AB$	$BA-9-(-8765-43)+2*1$
88A0	15096	$-1-2*34-(-5+67-89AB)$	$BA-9+8765+43+2+1$
88A1	15097	$1*234+567+89A*B$	$B+A9+8765-(-4*3-21)$
88A2	15098	$1+234+567-89A*-B$	$B+A9+8765+43-2*1$
88A3	15099	$-123-(4-5*6+7-89AB)$	$B+A9-(-8765-43+2-1)$
88A4	15100	$-123-45*6+7*(-8-9)*-AB$	$BA98+7*(-6-543)-21$
88A5	15101	$-123-4*5-6-(-7-89AB)$	$B-(-A9-8765)+43-(-2+1)$
88A6	15102	$-12-3-(45+67-89AB)$	$B+A9+8765+43+2*1$
88A7	15103	$-12-3*(45-6)-(-7-89AB)$	$-B+A9+8765+43+21$
88A8	15104	$1*2*(-3-4-5+678)*(9+A-B)$	$BA98-7*(6+543-(-2-1))$
88A9	15105	$12-3*45-(-6+7)+89AB$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4*3^2*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
88AA	15106	-123-45+67+89AB	-B+A9+8765+4-3*-21
88AB	15107	123+4*56+(7+89)*AB	B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5+4)+3-(2-1)
88B0	15108	-12+3-45-67+89AB	BA-(-9-8765)-(-43+2+1)
88B1	15109	1-2-345+6+7*(-8-9)*-AB	-BA+9876-543*2-1
88B2	15110	1+2-3*4+5*6*7*8*9+A-B	-BA-(-9876+543*-2*-1)
88B3	15111	123+45*-6+7+89AB	B+A*9+8765+43*2-1
88B4	15112	-1-2*3-45-67+89AB	BA+9-(-8765-43)-(-2+1)
88B5	15113	-12-34-5-67+89AB	BA+9876+5+4*-321
88B6	15114	-1-2-3*(45-6)+7+89AB	BA+9+8765+43+2+1
88B7	15115	1-2-(3+45+67-89AB)	B+A9*87-(6+5)-4*-321
88B8	15116	-12+34*-5-(-67-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4*3*2-1
88B9	15117	-1+2-3-45-(67-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4*3*2^1
88BA	15118	1+234+56*-7+89AB	BA-9-(-8765-43)+21
88BB	15119	1-(-2+3)-45-(67-89AB)	B+A*98*(7+6)-(5-4)*(-3-21)
8900	15120	-123+45-6-(7-89AB)	B+A+98+7+6*54*(32+1)
8901	15121	1-(2-3)-45-(67-89AB)	BA-9+8765+4+3*21
8902	15122	-1+2+34-(5+6)*(7*8-9AB)	B+A-9*-8*-7*-6*5-4*(3+2)+1
8903	15123	-12-(34-5)-67+89AB	B-A*-987-(6+5)*43*2*-1
8904	15124	-12-(34+56)-(7-89AB)	-B+A9*87-65*4*-3*-2*1
8905	15125	1-(-2-3)-(-45-67)-89AB)	B-(-A9-8765)-(-43-21)
8906	15126	1-23-4*5-67+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4*3*2-1
8907	15127	-12-(-3+4*-5*-6-7)+89AB	-BA+9876-(-54+3)*-21
8908	15128	-1-(-2+34+5+67-89AB)	-B+A9-(-8765-43*2+1)
8909	15129	1*2-34-5-67+89AB	-B+A9-(-8765+43*-2*1)
890A	15130	12-3-45-67+89AB	-B+A9+8765-43*-2+1
890B	15131	-1+2+34*-5-(-67-89AB)	BA+987-6*-5*(-4+321)
8910	15132	-123-(-45-6)-7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4-3-2^1
8911	15133	-123+45-(6-7)*89AB	BA+98-(76-5)*(-4-3)*21
8912	15134	-1-2-(34-5)-(67-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4*3/2-1
8913	15135	-1-2-34-56-7+89AB	-BA+987-6*543*(-2-1)
8914	15136	1-(2+34-5)-(-67-89AB)	BA+9-(-8765-43)+21
8915	15137	1-23-4-5-67+89AB	B+A9+8765+4*(-3+21)
8916	15138	-12-(34+56)+7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4+3-2^1
8917	15139	-1+2-34-56-7+89AB	BA98-765*(-4-(3-2))*-1
8918	15140	1-(-2+34-5)-(-67-89AB)	-B-A*-9+8765-4*32*-1
8919	15141	-1*(-2+3)*(-456-7-8*9)*(A+B)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4-3-2+1
891A	15142	1*2*(-3+4567-(8+9A)-B)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5-4+3+2^1
891B	15143	-123+4+56-(7-89AB)	BA-9+8765-(43*-2+1)
8920	15144	12+34*-5+67+89AB	BA-9-(-8765-43*2*1)
8921	15145	1-23+4-5-67+89AB	-B+A-9*-8*-7*-6*5+4-3+21
8922	15146	-1-(23+4)-(56+7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4+3-2^1
8923	15147	1+23-(45+67-89AB)	-B*(-A9-(8765)-(-4+3+2))*1
8924	15148	1-23-4-56-7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3/2+1
8925	15149	-123-4+56+7+89AB	-BA-9-87*-65+4321
8926	15150	-123-4-5+67+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4+3+2^1
8927	15151	12-34+5-67+89AB	B-(-A9-8765)-43*-2*1
8928	15152	12-34-56-7+89AB	-B-A9-8-76*-5*(-4+32*1)
8929	15153	-1-23+4+5-67+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4+3^2-1
892A	15154	-12-3-(-4+5)-(-67-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4+3^2*1
892B	15155	1+2-34-56+7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4+3^2+1
8930	15156	-1+2+3*-4-5-67+89AB	-B+A9+87*(-65+4)*(-3+2-1)
8931	15157	-123+4-(-56-7)+89AB	B+A+9-8+7+(6*5*4+3)^2-1
8932	15158	-123-(-4-(-5-(-67-89AB)))	-B*(-A-987+6-(-54+32+1))
8933	15159	1-23-45-6-(7-89AB)	-BA+9-8+76*5*(4-32)*-1
8934	15160	-1-23-4-(56-(7+89AB))	-B-A*-9+(87-6-54)*321
8935	15161	-1+2-(3+4+5+67-89AB)	BA+9+8765+43*2-1
8936	15162	1-(23+4+56)-(-7-89AB)	BA+9+8765+43*-2*-1
8937	15163	-1-2-(-3-(-4-5))-(-67-89AB)	BA-(-9-8765-(43*2+1))
8938	15164	-12-3-(-4-5-(-67+89AB))	B+A98+7+6*5*(-4+321)
8939	15165	-12-3+4-(56+7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3*2^1
893A	15166	12-34-(56-(7+89AB))	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3*2+1
893B	15167	1-(2+3-4+5+67-89AB)	-B+A9-87*-65+4321
8940	15168	-123+4+5+67+89AB	B+A+9*8*7+(6+5)^4+3-2+1
8941	15169	1+2+3-4-5-67+89AB	-B*(A-987+6-(-5-4)-(-3+2*1))
8942	15170	1-23-(-4+56)-(-7-89AB)	-BA-98*(-7+65-4)*(-3+2-1)
8943	15171	1+2-3+4-5-67+89AB	-BA+987*(6+5)-43-21
8944	15172	-1+2+3*-45-(-67-89AB)	BA+9+8765+4*(3+21)
8945	15173	1+2-3-4+5-67+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4^3/2^1
8946	15174	-12+3-(45+6+7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4^3/2+1
8947	15175	-1+2+3-(-4+5)-(-67-89AB)	-BA+9+8+76*5*(-4-32*-1)
8948	15176	-12*(3-4-5-678+9-AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3^2-1
8949	15177	-12+3-4-56+7+89AB	-B-A*-987-65+43*21
894A	15178	1-(2+3-4+56+7-89AB)	-B+A9+8765-4*-32-1
894B	15179	-12-(3-4-(-56+7+89AB))	-B-(-A9-8765+4*32*-1)
8950	15180	-1*-2*(-3-4-(56-7))*(-8-(9A-B))	B*A*(9-87*(-6+5)-(-43+21))
8951	15181	1-2-3-45-6-7+89AB	B-A*(-987-65-4-(32-1))
8952	15182	1-(-2+3)-(-4+56+7-89AB)	B+A*9+(-87+6+54)*-321
8953	15183	-12-3-4-5+6*-7+89AB	-B+A9+8765+4*(32+1)
8954	15184	12-3-4+5-(67-89AB)	B+A+(-9*-8+7*6)*(5+4^3*2)+1
8955	15185	1+2-(3+45)-6-(7-89AB)	B-A*-98-7*-65*(43-21)
8956	15186	-1+2+3+4-(56+7-89AB)	BA9-(8-7654-321)
8957	15187	-1*(-2-3-4+56+7-89AB)	-B+A*(987-6)-54*-321
8958	15188	12+3+4-5-67+89AB	B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5+4/3+2)-1
8959	15189	-1-(-23+4+5+67-89AB)	BA98+76*5*4*-3+21
895A	15190	-12*(3-(4+5+6+789-A+B))	BA-9+8765+4*(32-1)
895B	15191	-1-(2+3-(-45+6-7)-89AB)	-B*(A+987-65+43-2)*-1
8960	15192	12-3+4+5-67+89AB	-B-A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5+4/3)-(-2+1)
8961	15193	12-3+4-56-7+89AB	BA-9+8765-(4*-32+1)
8962	15194	-1+2-34-5-6-7+89AB	-BA*(-98+76-5-43-21)
8963	15195	1+2-(3-4)*-56+7+89AB	BA-(9-8765-4*32-1)
8964	15196	1-(-2+3)-(-4+56-7-89AB)	B+A-9+8*7+(6*5*4+3)^2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8965	15197	-1+2-3-45-6-(-7-89AB)	-B+A9-(-8+765)*(4+3)*-2+1
8966	15198	-1-2+3-45*(-6+7)+89AB	B+A-9+8*7+(6*5*4+3)^2+1
8967	15199	12-3-4-56+7+89AB	-B+A*-9+8*7*65+4321
8968	15200	-1-2-34-(-5+6+7)+89AB	B-(-A9-8765-4*32)-1
8969	15201	-1-23-4-(5+6)-(-7-89AB)	B+A9+8765+4*32*1
896A	15202	-12-34+5+(-6+7)*89AB	BA9-(-8-7654-321)
896B	15203	-12-34+5-6+7+89AB	BA9+8+7-65*(-4-3)*21
8970	15204	-1+2-34-(-5+6+7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3-2+1
8971	15205	12-(-3+4+56-7-89AB)	B+A-98+76*-5*(4-32*1)
8972	15206	1-(2+34+5+6)-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3+2-1
8973	15207	1-2-(3-(-45+6+7+89AB))	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3+2*1
8974	15208	-1+2-(-34+5)-6+7+89AB	B-A+9+8+765*(-4-3)*-2*1
8975	15209	-1-(23-4)-(-5+6+7-89AB)	-B+A9*(876-(5+4-321))
8976	15210	1+2+34-5-6+7+89AB	B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5+4-3)-(2+1)
8977	15211	-1-23-4+5-6-(-7-89AB)	-BA-9-(-8765+4-321)
8978	15212	-123+45+6+7+89AB	BA-9+87-6*54*(-32-1)
8979	15213	-1-23-(4+5-6)-(-7-89AB)	BA-(-9-8765-43*(2+1))
897A	15214	12+3-45+6-7+89AB	-B+A9-8*(-7-6+54)*(-32+1)
897B	15215	-1-2-(-34+56)-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9+8*7+(6*5*4+3)^2/1
8980	15216	1-2-(-34-(5-6+7+89AB))	B+A+9+8*7+(6*5*4+3)^2+1
8981	15217	12-(-3+4*(5+6)+7-89AB)	B+A9*87+6*-54*(-3-2)-1
8982	15218	-12+34-56+7+89AB	-B-A+(-9*(8-7*6)+5)*(4+3)^2*1
8983	15219	-1+2+34-56-7+89AB	-BA-9+8765-(-4-321)
8984	15220	1+2-(-34-(5-6)-89AB)	-BA+9*(8+765+432)-1
8985	15221	12-(34+5)-6-(-7-89AB)	-BA-9*(-8-765-432*1)
8986	15222	1+2-34-5+6+7+89AB	-B-A9+8765-4+321
8987	15223	-1+23-45-(-6+7)+89AB	BA98+7*(-6+543-2)*-1
8988	15224	1+23-(-4+56-7-89AB)	B*(A9-(-876+5+4)-(-3-21))
8989	15225	-1-(2-3-(45-6+7+89AB))	B+A+9-(8+7)*(6+5-4*(3+2))^1
898A	15226	-1-2-34+5+6-(-7-89AB)	-B-A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3*2-1
898B	15227	1234-567-89A*-B	B+A-9-(-8*(7-(-6-5*4)*3+2)+1)
8990	15228	-1*-23*(-456-78+9A*B)	B+A+9*8+7+(6*5*4+3)^2-1
8991	15229	12-(34-5-6)-(-7-89AB)	-BA+9+8765-4+321
8992	15230	-12+34-5+6*-7+89AB	-B-A9+8765-(-4-321)
8993	15231	12+34+5-6+7+89AB	-B-A+9876+543*2*-1
8994	15232	1+2-34+5+6+7+89AB	B+A+(-9-8*7)*(-6-5*4)*3^2+1
8995	15233	-1+2-(-34+56)-(-7-89AB)	-B*-A+9*8*7*6*5+4-3+2*1
8996	15234	-12-(34+5*-6)-(-7-89AB)	BA98-7*(-6+543)+21
8997	15235	1-(2+3-(-4+5))-(-6-(-7+89AB))	-B*(-A98+76+5+43+21)
8998	15236	12-3-(-45+67-89AB)	B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5+4/3)-(2-1)
8999	15237	-1+2-3-4-(-5+6-(-7+89AB))	-BA+9+8765+4+321
899A	15238	-12-3-4-5+6+7+89AB	-B-A*(9+8)*76+(5-4*-3)*(-2-1)
899B	15239	1-23-4+5+6+7+89AB	-B-(-A-98*76-54*-3*-21)
89A0	15240	-12+3-4+5-(-6+7-89AB)	B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5-4*3+2-1)
89A1	15241	-1+2-3-4-(-5+6)+7+89AB	BA+98+7+6*-54*(-32-1)
89A2	15242	12+3+45-6+7+89AB	B+A+(-9*-8*-7*-6+5*4)*(3+2)+1
89A3	15243	12-34-(-5-6-7-89AB)	-B-A+9*8*(7*6*5-4+3*2)^1
89A4	15244	1+2+3*(-4+5)-6-7+89AB	B-A9+8765-4+321
89A5	15245	-12-3*-4-5-(6-7-89AB)	B+A+((9/-8+7)*6^5-4*3)/(2+1)
89A6	15246	1-(-23+4*5)-(6+7-89AB)	-B*(-A-98)*(-7-6*5+43-2-1)
89A7	15247	1*(-2-3+4)*(5+6-(-7+89AB))	B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5-4*3)-2/1
89A8	15248	12-(3-4+5+6+7-89AB)	B+A+(-9+8*7)*(-6-(-5*4*3+2))-1
89A9	15249	12+3*-4-(5+6)-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+4*3*(2+1)
89AA	15250	1-2-(-3456+7)-8*-9*AB	B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6*(-5-4)*3*2+1
89AB	15251	1+2-34-5*-6+7+89AB	BA-9*-8*-7*6*-5+4*-3+2-1
89B0	15252	12-3-4-5-(-6+7-89AB)	B-A9+8765-(-4-321)
89B1	15253	1+23+45-6+7+89AB	B-A+9876+543*2*-1
89B2	15254	12-3-4-(5+6)-(-7-89AB)	B-A+9876-543*2+1
89B3	15255	-1+2+3-4+5+6-7+89AB	B+A9*(87+6-5)-4*-321
89B4	15256	12+3-4+5-6-(7-89AB)	B+A+(-9-8*7)*6+5*(4+3-2+1)
89B5	15257	-1+2+3-4+5-6+7+89AB	-B*(-A-987-6*(5-4)-(-3-21))
89B6	15258	-1+23+4-5*6+7+89AB	B+A-987*(6-5)-4*32*1
89B7	15259	-12-(-34-(-5-6))-(-7-89AB)	B+A-9*8+7*6*(5+4)^3/2+1
89B8	15260	-12-3-(45-67-89AB)	B+A*(987+65+43-2)-1
89B9	15261	-1-(-2+3-4+5-6-7-89AB)	BA98+76*-54+321
89BA	15262	12-3-4+5-(-6+7)+89AB	B+A-9+(-8-7*6)*-5*(4^3-(2+1))
89BB	15263	12-3-4+5+(-6+7)*89AB	B+A*-987-6+54*321
8A00	15264	12-3-(4-5+6)-(-7-89AB)	B+A-9*(-8*(-7*-6*5+4/3)-(2+1))
8A01	15265	-1-2+3*4+5+(-6+7)*89AB	-B-A+(-9-8)*7*6+(-5*-4)^3*2/1
8A02	15266	-12-(-3+45)-(-67-89AB)	B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5-4*3-2)-1
8A03	15267	1+2+3+4-(-5-(-6+7))+89AB	B+A-9*(-8*7*6*5-4*3-2)^1
8A04	15268	1-23-4+5-6*-7+89AB	-B*(-A-(987-6-5-4-3*-2*-1))
8A05	15269	1-2-34-(-56-(-7+89AB))	-B+A*-9+8765+4+321
8A06	15270	-12-34-(-56-7)+89AB	-B-A-9-87*-65+4321
8A07	15271	-12-34-5+6+7+89AB	B+A+9-8+7*6-(5*4^3)^2*1
8A08	15272	1*2-(34-56)-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9876+543*-2-1
8A09	15273	1-(2-(-3-45)-(-67+89AB))	B+A+9876+543*2*-1
8A0A	15274	-12-3+45-6-7+89AB	B+A+9876+543*-2+1
8A0B	15275	-1-23+45+6-7+89AB	-B-A+9-8*(7-6*-5*-4^3+2)-1
8A10	15276	1+2+34-5-6-7+89AB	B+A+9*8-7*(6-(5+4)^3)*(2+1)
8A11	15277	1+23-(-4+5-6+7-89AB)	BA+9*87-6*54*(-32+1)
8A12	15278	-1-23-4-(-56+7-89AB)	-B-A+9/8*7*6^5/4-3^2-1
8A13	15279	1+2345-(67+8*-9AB)	B*(A+9-8-7+654+321)
8A14	15280	-12+3+45-6-7+89AB	-BA+987*(6+5)-4-(-32+1)
8A15	15281	-12+34+5+6-7+89AB	B+A-(-9-8*7-6*5^4)*(3+2-1)
8A16	15282	12+3-(4-5-6-7-89AB)	B+A+9+(-8*-7+6)*(5*(4+3)^2+1)
8A17	15283	1-2-34+56+7+89AB	B-A-9*(-876+5-4-321)
8A18	15284	-12-34*(5-6)+7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7*6*5+(4*3)^2-1
8A19	15285	-1-(-23-4)-(-5-6+7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*(7*6*5-4+3*2)^1
8A1A	15286	-1-23+4+56-7+89AB	-B+A-987*(-6-5)-43*-2*-1
8A1B	15287	-1+2+3*4+5*6-7+89AB	B+A+9+8+7*6-(5*4^3)^2*1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8A20	15288	$12^*(-3+4-(-56+7+8^*(-9A-B)))$	$-B-(A-9)-(87^*-65-4321)$
8A21	15289	$-1+23+4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8-7^*-6^*((5+4)^3/2-1)$
8A22	15290	$-1-(-2345-6789)-AB$	$B^*-A^*(-98+7-(-6-(-54+3+21)))$
8A23	15291	$-1^*(-2345-6789+AB)$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8-7^*-6^*-5^*4)+3)^2*1$
8A24	15292	$-1-23-4+56+7+89AB$	$BA9-876^*-5+4321$
8A25	15293	$1-2+3+45-(6+7)+89AB$	$B+A-((-9^*-8-7^*6^*(5+4)^3)/2+1)$
8A26	15294	$12-(-3+45-67)+89AB$	$B+A+9^*(8+7+(6-5^*(-4-3))^2+1)$
8A27	15295	$-12+34+5+6-(-7-89AB)$	$B-(A-9876)-5^*4^*-3^*-21$
8A28	15296	$-1+2-3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8^7)^*((6^*-5+4)^3*2-1)$
8A29	15297	$-1-2-(3-45)-(-6+7-89AB)$	$BA9-8^*(-765-432+1)$
8A2A	15298	$12-34+56+7+89AB$	$-B-A+9/8^7*6^5/4+3^2+1$
8A2B	15299	$12-34-5+6+7+89AB$	$-B+A-9^*(-876-5+4-321)$
8A30	15300	$-12-(3-45-6)-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9-8^*(7-6^5*4^3+2)^1$
8A31	15301	$-1-23+4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B^*(A98+76^*5-432-1)$
8A32	15302	$1-23-(-4-56-7)+89AB$	$B-A9-8+7^*(6-54)^*-32^*1$
8A33	15303	$1-23-(-4+5-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3^A(2+1)$
8A34	15304	$1+2-3+45^*(-6+7)+89AB$	$BA9+8^*(765+432)-1$
8A35	15305	$1-23-4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8-7^*-6^*((5+4)^3/2-1)$
8A36	15306	$1-(-23-4+5^*6)-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(9/(8-7)+6)^*(-5+4^A(3+2))^1$
8A37	15307	$-1+2-(-3-45-6+7-89AB)$	$BA98-7-(-6-54)^*3^*-21$
8A38	15308	$-12-3^*-4+56-(-7-89AB)$	$-B+A+9+87^*65+4321$
8A39	15309	$12+34+5+6-7+89AB$	$B+A+(9+8+7)^*(6+5^4+3^2)^1$
8A3A	15310	$-12+3-4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B-(A-9+87^*-65-4321)$
8A3B	15311	$-1-23-(-4-5)-(-67-89AB)$	$B+A-9^*(8+7)-(-6^5+4^3)^2+1$
8A40	15312	$-1^*(23-4-5-67-89AB)$	$-B^*(A98-765-4-3)^*(-2-1)$
8A41	15313	$1+2345+6789+A^*-B$	$BA9-8^*(-765-432-1)$
8A42	15314	$-1-2-3-4+56+7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8^7+6^5-4^3)^2-1$
8A43	15315	$-1+2-3+45+6+7+89AB$	$-B-A+987^*(6+5)-43-2^*1$
8A44	15316	$12-3+45-6+7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8^7+6^5-4^3)^2+1$
8A45	15317	$-12+3+4+56+7+89AB$	$-BA+9-87^*6^*(-54+32+1)$
8A46	15318	$-1^*(-2-(3-4^*-5+6^*7+89AB))$	$BA9-(-8-7-6^*-5^*(4-321))$
8A47	15319	$1-(2-(3+45+6)-(-7+89AB))$	$B+A+9-8^7*6^5+4^3+2+1$
8A48	15320	$-1-(2-3+4-56-7-89AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3^2-1$
8A49	15321	$12+3+45^*(-6+7)+89AB$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7^*6^5+4-3/2)^1$
8A4A	15322	$12+3-(-45+6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3^2+1$
8A4B	15323	$1-2-(-3+4+5)-(-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3^2-1$
8A50	15324	$-1+2^*-3+4^*-56-7^*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3^2*1$
8A51	15325	$-1-(2-(-3-4+5+6+7+89AB))$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3-2^1$
8A52	15326	$1+2+3-4+56+7+89AB$	$BA-98+76^*5^*(-4+32)^*1$
8A53	15327	$1-2-3-4+5+6+7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(-8765+4^3*21)$
8A54	15328	$12-3+45-(-6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3+2-1$
8A55	15329	$-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4-3+2^1$
8A56	15330	$1-2+3+4+56+7+89AB$	$B+A+9-87^*-65+4321$
8A57	15331	$12+3+4+56-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4+3-2/1$
8A58	15332	$-1+2-(-3-4-56-7-89AB)$	$-B-A-9+8765-4+321$
8A59	15333	$1+23-(-45+6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7^*6^5+4/3^2)^1$
8A5A	15334	$123-4-(5+67-89AB)$	$-B^*(-A9-8-(-7-6-5-43^*-21))$
8A5B	15335	$1^*(-2+3)^*4^*-5^*-67-89^*-AB$	$-B-A^*98+7^*6^*(-54+321)$
8A60	15336	$-12-(-34-56)-7+89AB$	$-BA^*(-98+7+65-43-21)$
8A61	15337	$-1+2-3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4+3^2+1$
8A62	15338	$12+3-4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A^*(-9-8)^*-76+54-32+1$
8A63	15339	$-1-2-(-3-(4+5))-(-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9/8^7*6^5/4+3^2/1$
8A64	15340	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4567-8^*-9+A^*-B)$	$-B-(A+9-8765-4-321)$
8A65	15341	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9+(8+7+6)^*(5+4)^3+2^1$
8A66	15342	$12-3-4+5+6+7+89AB$	$BA-9+8765+4^3*21$
8A67	15343	$-1+23+45-(-6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9+8^*(7+6+5^4)^3+2-1$
8A68	15344	$123-4-(-5-(-67+89AB))$	$B-A^*-9^*(8+7^*-6)^*-5-4-(-32+1)$
8A69	15345	$123-(4+56)-(-7-89AB)$	$-B^*(-A98-(-76+5)-(-43-21))$
8A6A	15346	$1+2^*3+4-(-5-(67+89AB))$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^*(5+4)^3/2-1$
8A6B	15347	$-1-(-23+4)-(-5-67)+89AB$	$BA9+8765+43^*-21$
8A70	15348	$-1^*(-234-(-5+678))^*(-9+A+B)$	$B+A+9+8+7^*6^*(5+4)^3/2+1$
8A71	15349	$1-2+3+4+56-7+89AB$	$B-(A9-8765-4^*-3^*-21)$
8A72	15350	$12-3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$-B-A+9+8765-4+321$
8A73	15351	$-12+3+4^*5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9+8^7-6^5+4^3)^*-2/1$
8A74	15352	$1-23+4^*5^*6+7+89AB$	$-B+A-9-(-8765+4-321)$
8A75	15353	$123+4-(56+7-89AB)$	$B+A-(9+(-8-7)^*(-6/5+4^A(3+2))+1)$
8A76	15354	$-1+23-(-4-(56+7))+89AB$	$B-A-9+8765-(4-321)$
8A77	15355	$-1-(-23-4+5-67-89AB)$	$BA9-8-7^*(65+4-3)^*-21$
8A78	15356	$-12-3+4-(56-7^*89^*(A+B))$	$-B^*(-A9-876-54+32+1)$
8A79	15357	$-1-(-23+4-5-67-89AB)$	$-B+A98^*7-6^*(-543+21)$
8A7A	15358	$1-2345^*(6-7)+8^*9AB$	$-B-A+9+8765+4+321$
8A7B	15359	$123-4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A-9^*8+(-7+6^5-4^3)^2*1$
8A80	15360	$1+2^*3^*4+5+6+7+89AB$	$BA-(-9-8765+4^3*21)$
8A81	15361	$12-3+4^*5-(-67-89AB)$	$-B-A+9^*8+7^*6^*(5+4)^3/2+1$
8A82	15362	$-1-(2-34)-(-5-67-89AB)$	$B-A-9+8765+4+321$
8A83	15363	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A-9+(8+7+6)^*((5+4)^3+2^1)$
8A84	15364	$1-(2-34+5)-(-67-89AB)$	$-B+A-(-987^*(6+5)-4+3+21)$
8A85	15365	$-12-3+4^*-5^*(67-8)+9^*AB$	$-B-A+9876+54^*(3-21)$
8A86	15366	$-12-3-(-45-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8^*(7^*6^5+4^3)^2(2-1)$
8A87	15367	$123-(-4+56-7)+89AB$	$B^*(A+987-(-6-(-5-(-4-3))))^*(2-1)$
8A88	15368	$1+2+3+4-5+6+7+89AB$	$B+A-((-9-8^*-7^*6+(-5^*4)^3)^2-1)$
8A89	15369	$-1+23+4+5+6+7-8^*-9AB$	$-B-A^*(9-8)^*(-765+4-321)$
8A8A	15370	$123-45-6+7+89AB$	$-B+A+9-(-8765+4-321)$
8A8B	15371	$1+23+4+5+6+7+8^*9AB$	$-BA-9+8765-(-432+1)$
8A90	15372	$-12+3+4+5+6+7+89AB$	$B-A+9+8765-4+321$
8A91	15373	$-1-(-2+3+4^*-5+6+7)+89AB$	$-BA-(9-8765)-(-432-1)$
8A92	15374	$1-2-3-4^*5^*-6+7+89AB$	$B+A-9+8765-4+321$
8A93	15375	$1+2+3+4^*5-6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9+(-8-7)^*(6-5-4^A(3+2^1))$
8A94	15376	$1^*-2^*(-3-4567-(89-AB))$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*(-7^*-6^5+4)+3^2)+1$
8A95	15377	$1234-56+789A+B$	$-B-A+(-9-8^7+6^5-4^3)^2*1$
8A96	15378	$1+2+3+4-(-5-67-89AB)$	$-B+A+9+8765+4+321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8A97	15379	$1-2-3-(-45-(67+89AB))$	$B+A987+65*(-4-32-1)$
8A98	15380	$1-(2-3-4*5*6-7)+89AB$	$B-(A-(9+8765))-(-4-321)$
8A99	15381	$123-(4-(5+6*-7+89AB))$	$B+A+9*8*(7*6*5+4/3+2)^{\wedge}1$
8A9A	15382	$123-45+6+7+89AB$	$-B-A9-(-8765-432)-1$
8A9B	15383	$-1-2+3+45+67+89AB$	$-B-A9+8765-432*-1$
8AA0	15384	$-1-(234-56*7-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8765+432+1$
8AA1	15385	$1+2*(-3+4567-8-9-A+B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*(-7*6*5+4)+3+2)+1$
8AA2	15386	$1-234+56*7+89AB$	$B+A-9*8-((-7-(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3))*2+1)$
8AA3	15387	$-1+2-(-3-45-67)+89AB$	$B-A+9876-54*(-3+21)$
8AA4	15388	$-1234+56+78*9*(A+B)$	$B+A-9+(8-7+6*5*4+3)^{\wedge}2/1$
8AA5	15389	$12+34+5+6+7+89AB$	$B*(A9+876-5-(4-32)-1)$
8AA6	15390	$1+2*3+45+67+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765+432*1$
8AA7	15391	$-123-45*-6-7+89AB$	$-BA+9+8765+432+1$
8AA8	15392	$(-1-2/3-(-4-5*6*7)*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A-(-9-(8765-4)-321)$
8AA9	15393	$12+34*-5*(-67+8)-9*-AB$	$-B-(-A-9876-(5+43))*-21$
8AAA	15394	$12-3+45+67+89AB$	$BA+9876-543*-2*-1$
8AAB	15395	$1-(-2-3^{\wedge}(-4+5+6))^{*7+8*9+A-B}$	$BA-(-9876+543*2)+1$
8AB0	15396	$123-(-45+67-89AB)$	$B+A+(9*8*7-6-5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8AB1	15397	$-12-3*-45-6+7+89AB$	$-B-A*9*8+7*-6*-54*-3*2*1$
8AB2	15398	$-1+2345+6*7-8*-9AB$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6*5*4-3)^{\wedge}2*1$
8AB3	15399	$-1+2*(34-5)+67+89AB$	$-B-A*(9-8+7-(6+543*2)-1)$
8AB4	15400	$-1+2345+6789-A-B$	$B+A-(-9-8765-4-321)$
8AB5	15401	$123-4*5+6-7+89AB$	$B-A*-9-87*-65+4321$
8AB6	15402	$1+2345-(-6789+A+B)$	$-BA+98*(7+65+43-2+1)$
8AB7	15403	$123-4*5-(6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+7*6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3/2+1$
8AB8	15404	$((1-2^{\wedge}3+4)^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7-8*9)+A-B$	$B-(A9-8765)+432-1$
8AB9	15405	$-123+45*6+7+89AB$	$B-A9+8765-432*-1$
8ABA	15406	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(-4-5*-6*7+8)*9+A-B$	$B-A9+8765-(-432-1)$
8ABB	15407	$-12-34-5*-6*7+89AB$	$B+A+9876+54*(3-21)$
8B00	15408	$-1-2-3*(4+567-89A)*B$	$B+A+9+(-8-7)*(-6/5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)/1)$
8B01	15409	$-12+3-(4+5+6)-7*89*(-A-B)$	$B+A+9+(-8-7)*(-6/5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
8B02	15410	$123-4+5-6-7+89AB$	$B+A-9*(-8-7*(6+5*4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
8B03	15411	$1+23-(-45-67-89AB)$	$B*(A-987+6+5*4-32)*-1$
8B04	15412	$1234-5+6-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9+8*(7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}1$
8B05	15413	$1+2345-67+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+9+8+(-7-6*5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
8B06	15414	$123-4-5-6+7+89AB$	$B-A-987*(-6-5)-4-(-3-21)$
8B07	15415	$-1*2*3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-(-5-43)*-21$
8B08	15416	$1234+5*-67-89*-AB$	$-BA-9-8+7*(65-4*-3)*21$
8B09	15417	$1+234*(56-(-7-(89-AB)))$	$BA9*(8-7+6-5*4-3+21)$
8B0A	15418	$123+4+5-6-7+89AB$	$-B+A9-87*-65+4321$
8B0B	15419	$(1+2)*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6^{\wedge}5-4*3)*2^{\wedge}1$
8B10	15420	$-1+2345-(-6789-A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6^{\wedge}5-4*3)*2+1$
8B11	15421	$-1+2345-6789*(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8*(7*6*5+4-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
8B12	15422	$123-4+5+6-(7-89AB)$	$B*(A98-76+54*(-3+2))^*1$
8B13	15423	$12-(-34+56-7*-89*(-A-B))$	$B+A*-98*-7-65+4321$
8B14	15424	$1-(-2345-6789A)+B$	$-B-(-A-987*(6+5)+4*-3*(2+1))$
8B15	15425	$123-4+(-5-6)*(-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)*2^{\wedge}1$
8B16	15426	$1+2+3*4+5+6-(-7-89AB)$	$BA98-7*(-6+5*4*(32-1))$
8B17	15427	$1+2-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-((-8*-7-6^{\wedge}5+4*3)*2+1)$
8B18	15428	$-1*2*(-3-4567)*(-8+9)*(-A+B)$	$B+A-9-8*(7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
8B19	15429	$1+23-4-5*6+7*-89*(-A-B)$	$B-A-98*(-7-6+5*4*3*2*-1)$
8B1A	15430	$123+4-(-5-6)-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8*(7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}1$
8B1B	15431	$123+4+5-(-6+7)*-89AB$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6*(-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2)))+1$
8B20	15432	$123+4-(-5-(-6+7)-89AB)$	$B-A-987*(-6-5)-(-4+32*-1)$
8B21	15433	$123+45+6*-7+89AB$	$B-A-9-(-87*65-4321)$
8B22	15434	$1234-5+6+789A+B$	$-B+A987-65*(4+32)*1$
8B23	15435	$-1+2345+67+8*9AB$	$-B+A987-65*(4+32)+1$
8B24	15436	$-12+34*5+6-7+89AB$	$BA+9876-5*-4*-3*21$
8B25	15437	$1+2345+67-8*-9AB$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*(6-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2*1)$
8B26	15438	$-1*2*3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*(6-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
8B27	15439	$1-23+4-5*-6*7+89AB$	$-B-A*(9-(8-(-765-4))-321)$
8B28	15440	$-1*-2*34*(-5+6)*(78-(9-A*B))$	$B+A9+8*7*65+4321$
8B29	15441	$123-4+5*6-7+89AB$	$-B-A*-9-(-8765+4-321)$
8B2A	15442	$-1+2345+6789A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6^{\wedge}5/(4-3))^*2-1$
8B2B	15443	$-1*(-2345-6789-(A+B))$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4+3*2)/1$
8B30	15444	$1+2345+6789A+B$	$-B-(-A+9+8*7*-6*(5-43))-2*1$
8B31	15445	$((1-2)^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7+8)+9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(9*-8+7+6^{\wedge}5+4-3)*2*1$
8B32	15446	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9*-8+7+6^{\wedge}5+4-3)*2+1$
8B33	15447	$-1+234-5*-6*-7*-8*9*(-A+B)$	$B+A+((9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)*2^{\wedge}1$
8B34	15448	$123-45+67+89AB$	$BA+98-765*(4+3)*2*-1$
8B35	15449	$123+4+5*6-7+89AB$	$-B-A*-9+8765+4+321$
8B36	15450	$-12+34*5-(-6-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9+(-8*-7-(6^{\wedge}5-(4-3)))^*-2/1$
8B37	15451	$-1-2-3-4+5*6*7+89AB$	$BA-(-9-8*7*65)+4321$
8B38	15452	$-1*2*3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7-(-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)*2-1$
8B39	15453	$-1-2+(3-4-(5+6))^*(-7-89A-B)$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$
8B3A	15454	$1+2+34*5+(-6+7)*89AB$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$
8B3B	15455	$123-4-5*-6-(-7-89AB)$	$-B*(A98-(76+54-3))^*(-2+1)$
8B40	15456	$12*-3*(-45-67-89-AB)$	$B+A987-65*(4+32)*1$
8B41	15457	$1+2*(34+56)-7+89AB$	$B+A+(-9+8+7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)*2^{\wedge}1$
8B42	15458	$((1^{\wedge}2-3/4)^{\wedge}5+6)^*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)*2+1$
8B43	15459	$1-(-2-3*-4*(5-6)*(7+89A+B))$	$-B+A-(-987*(6+5)+4)-3*-21$
8B44	15460	$-123+4567-8*9*A*-B$	$B+A-9-8*(7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3*2)^{\wedge}1$
8B45	15461	$1-23+4*(56-7)+89AB$	$B+A+(-9+8-7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)*-2/1$
8B46	15462	$123-(-45-(-6-7)-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8*(7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}1$
8B47	15463	$123+4-5-6*-7+89AB$	$B+A*9-(-8765+4)+321$
8B48	15464	$1+2-(34-56)-7*89*(-A-B)$	$B+A+(-9*(-8+7)+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)*2+1$
8B49	15465	$-1+2-34*-5-(-6-7)+89AB$	$-BA+987-6*54*(-32+1)$
8B4A	15466	$1*2-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6^{\wedge}5+4*3)*2-1$
8B4B	15467	$1-2+3+4+5*6*7+89AB$	$-B-A*-98*7-6-5+4321$
8B50	15468	$1*2*(3+4567+8-9-(-A-B))$	$-B+A987+(65+43)*-21$
8B51	15469	$1+2*(-3+4567-89+AB)$	$-B-A9*(8-76-(-5+4)-32+1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
8B52	15470	-12-3-4*(-56+7)+89AB	B+A-9+8*7*-6*(5-43)-2*-1
8B53	15471	-123-4-5*-67+89AB	-B+A-(9-8*-7*6*(5-43)-21)
8B54	15472	-1-2+3*(456+7)*8+9-A*B	B+A-9*8+(-7+6^5-4-3)*2-1
8B55	15473	123+4-(-5+6*-7-89AB)	B+A-9*8+(-7+6^5-4-3)*2^1
8B56	15474	123+45+6-(7-89AB)	B+A-9*8+(-7+6^5-4-3)*2+1
8B57	15475	-12+3*45+67+89AB	B+A+9+8+(7+6^5-4^3)*2-1
8B58	15476	123+45-6-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9+8+(-7-6^5+4^3)*-2*1
8B59	15477	123-4+56-7+89AB	-B*(-A98-(-76-5-43-2-1))
8B5A	15478	1-(-2+3-4*5+(-6-(7+89)))*AB)	-BA*(9+8)*(76+5-4*-3+2*1)
8B5B	15479	-123+4-5*-67+89AB	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4+3*2)+1
8B60	15480	-1*2*(-3-4567-(-89+AB))	-B+A9-(-8765+4)+321
8B61	15481	1+23*45+67+89A*B	B+A-9-8*(7-6^5/4)-3^1(2+1)
8B62	15482	12+3+4-(-5*6*7-89AB)	-BA-9*8*-7*(6+54-32-1)
8B63	15483	123-4+5*(6+7)+89AB	B+A+9-(-8*-7-6^5-4-3)*2-1
8B64	15484	12*(34+56-78)*(-9*-A-B)	B+A+9+(-8-7-6^5+4^3)*-2^1
8B65	15485	123+4-(-56+7)+89AB	-B+A*987+6-5*4*-3*2^1
8B66	15486	-1+2+3*(4-5+67)+89AB	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4+3+2^1)
8B67	15487	1234+56+789A-B	B+A+9+8*7*6*(5*4+3)*2+1
8B68	15488	123-(-45-6-7-89AB)	-B-(-A9-8765-4-321)
8B69	15489	-1+2345+6-(7-89*A*B)	B-A*98*-7-6-5+4321
8B6A	15490	-1+2-(3*-45-67)+89AB	B-A-98*(7-65)+4321
8B6B	15491	123-4+56+7+89AB	B+A-9*8+(-7-6^5+4*3)*-2/1
8B70	15492	123-4-5+67+89AB	-B-A-9+8765+432-1
8B71	15493	-1-2-3^4+5^6-7*8+9+A-B	B-A98*-7+6*5*43*(2+1)
8B72	15494	-1-23*(-4-5)-(6-7)+89AB	-B-A-9+8765+432+1
8B73	15495	1*234-5-(67-89AB)	BA-9+8765-4+321
8B74	15496	1+234-(-5+67)+89AB	B+A-9-8*(7-6^5/4+3/2)^1
8B75	15497	-12-(-3-4*5^6)-7+89AB	-BA9-8*-7*-65*-4+32*-1
8B76	15498	12-3-(4*(-56+7)-89AB)	-BA9+8*7*-65*-4-32+1
8B77	15499	123+4-(-56-7-89AB)	B*(-A9-8+765-(-4-321))
8B78	15500	123-(-4+5-67-89AB)	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4+3)-2/1
8B79	15501	-1-2*3-4*-56-(7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*(7*6*5+4+3-2)^1
8B7A	15502	123-4-(-5-(67+89AB))	B+A9+8765-4+321
8B7B	15503	12-3*-45+67+89AB	BA-9-(-8765-4)+321
8B80	15504	-1+234+5-67+89AB	B+A98*7+6*543-21
8B81	15505	-1+234-56-7+89AB	B+A-9*8+7-(-6^5+4-3)*2-1
8B82	15506	1+234+5-67+89AB	B+A*987+6*5*43-21
8B83	15507	1+234-56-7+89AB	B+A-9*8+7-6^5*(4-3*2)-1
8B84	15508	-1+23+45-6+7*89*(A+B)	B+A-9-8*7-6^5*(4-3*2^1)
8B85	15509	1234+56+789A+B	B+A-9-8*(7-6^5/4)+3-2*1
8B86	15510	123+4-(-5-67)+89AB	-B*-A*(9-8+7-(6-54)+3*2^1)
8B87	15511	-12-(-3-4*5^6-(7+89AB))	-B-A+9+8765-432*-1
8B88	15512	12*(34-56-(-789-A-B))	-B-A-(-9-(8765-(-432-1)))
8B89	15513	1-23-456*(-7-8-9)+AB	-B+A-9+8765-432*-1
8B8A	15514	1+2-(-3+4*-56+7-89AB)	B-A-9+8765+432-1
8B8B	15515	-1*(23-4*-5+6+78)*(-9A+B)	B-A-9+8765-432*-1
8B90	15516	-12-34*-5+67+89AB	B-A-9+8765+432+1
8B91	15517	-1-2+34*56+78*(9+AB)	B+A+9+8*(7+6*5+4+3)^2-1
8B92	15518	1-2-3^4+5^6-7-8-9+A-B	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4+3-2^1)
8B93	15519	-1+234-56+7+89AB	B+A+9+8*(7+6*5+4+3)^2+1
8B94	15520	-1-(-2+3)+4*56+7+89AB	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4)-3*2*1
8B95	15521	1+234-(56-7-89AB)	B*(A9-87+654+321)
8B96	15522	1-2*(-3-45-67)+89AB	B+A-9-8*7+(6^5+4+3)*2/1
8B97	15523	1+2*(-3+4567)+89-A+B	-B+A+9876+5-43*21
8B98	15524	1-23+4*-5*-67-89A*-B	BA98+76*(-5-43)*(2-1)
8B99	15525	12+3-4*-56-(7-89AB)	B-A+9876+5-43*21
8B9A	15526	-1-2*3*-45+6*-7+89AB	B-A98*-7+6*543-(2+1)
8B9B	15527	1-2+3456+7*(-8-9A)*-B	B+A98*7+6*543+2*-1
8BA0	15528	1+2+3+4*56-(-7-89AB)	BA9-8-(7-6*5*(4+321))
8BA1	15529	1-2-34*-5+67+89AB	-BA9-8*-7*65*4-(3+2+1)
8BA2	15530	12-34-5-(6+7*89)*(-A-B)	-B+A+9+8765-(-432+1)
8BA3	15531	-1+2345+6789-A*-B	BA+987*(6-5)*(4-3*-2+1)
8BA4	15532	-1*-2*(345+67-89A)*-B	B*(-A+987-(-65+43)-2-1)
8BA5	15533	1+2345+6789A*B	B+A*987+6*5*43-2*-1
8BA6	15534	1*-2-3-456*(-7-8-9)+AB	B+A*987+6*5*43+2+1
8BA7	15535	123-4*-5*6-7+89AB	B+A+9876-(-5+43*21)
8BA8	15536	1-23-45*-6-7+89AB	B-(-A+9)+8765-(-432-1)
8BA9	15537	1-2-3-4+5^6-7-8*9+A-B	B-A*-987-(6+543*-2*1)
8BAA	15538	-123-(-4+56*-7-89AB)	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4-3/2)^1
8BAB	15539	1-23*4-5*-67+89AB	B+A+(-9+8*7+6^5-4^3)*2*1
8BB0	15540	12*(34+5+678+9*(A+B))	-BA9-8*7*-65*4+3*2-1
8BB1	15541	-1+2-3+4*(56+7)+89AB	-BA9-8*-7*-65*-4-(-3-2-1)
8BB2	15542	-1*-2*(3-4+(-5+67)*89)*(A-B)	-B+A987-6*(54+321)
8BB3	15543	1*(-2+34-5)*(678+9AB)	B*(A-9)*(-876+543)*(-2-1)
8BB4	15544	12+34*5+67+89AB	B+A+9*(8-7*6+5^4)*3-2*1
8BB5	15545	1-(-2-3-4*(56+7))+89AB	B+A-(-9876-5+43*21)
8BB6	15546	-123-(-4-56*7)+89AB	B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4-(3/2+1))
8BB7	15547	1-(-2+3)-(-4*(-5+67)-89AB)	B+A+9-8+(-7+6^5-4-3)*2+1
8BB8	15548	-1-(-23+4*-56)-(-7-89AB)	B+A-9-8*(7-6^5/4-3*2+1)
8BB9	15549	1+2+3-4*(-56-7)+89AB	B-A*-987+6-543*-2*1
8BBA	15550	-1+2345-6*(-7-8)*(9A+B)	B+A*987-(-6-543*2-1)
8BBB	15551	1-2-3-4+5^6+7-8*9+A-B	B+A+9-8*(7+6)+5^4(4+3-2+1)
9000	15552	-1+2345-(-6789-AB)	B-(-A-9-8765-432+1)
9001	15553	-1*(2345-6789-AB)	B+A98-7*6*(5+4)*(-32+1)
9002	15554	123+45-(-67-89AB)	-B*(-A-(987+6-5+4)-3+2+1)
9003	15555	-1-(-234+5*6-7-89AB)	-B+A*98*7-(-65-4321)
9004	15556	1234+5*-6*(-7-8)*(9A+B)	-BA9-8-76*54*-3-2-1
9005	15557	1*-2-3-45*-6-7+89AB	-BA9-8-76*-54*3+2*-1
9006	15558	1*2*(-34+567*8+9AB)	BA+98+76*5*(4-32)*1
9007	15559	-12-3-(45+67)*(-89-AB)	-B+A98+7*-65*(4-(-3+21))
9008	15560	-1+234-5-(6+7-89AB)	B+A+(-9+8+7+6^5-4*3)*2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9009	15561	$1*234-5-6-(7-89AB)$	$-BA9-(8-76*54*3)+2*1$
900A	15562	$1+234-5-6-7+89AB$	$BA-9*8*7*6*5-4*3*21$
900B	15563	$1+2-3+4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A-987*(-6-5)-43*(-2-1)$
9010	15564	$12+3-4*(5-67)+89AB$	$B+A987+6*(-54-321)$
9011	15565	$-12-3456-(7+8)*-9AB$	$B+A+98-7*(6-54)*32*1$
9012	15566	$-123-45*67-89*-A*B$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4-3*2+1)$
9013	15567	$1*2-3*4+5^6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8-7-6^5*(4-3*2)^1$
9014	15568	$-1*(2-3+4-(-5-6))*(-789-(A-B))$	$B+A+9-8+7-(-6^5+4+3)*2+1$
9015	15569	$-1+2345+67-89*-A*B$	$-B+A*987+6*5*(43+2)*-1$
9016	15570	$-1+234-(-5+6)-(7-89AB)$	$BA-98*7*(6-54+32+1)$
9017	15571	$1+2345+67+89*-A*-B$	$-B-A9*87-(6-543)*(2+1)$
9018	15572	$-1-(-234+5-6+7)+89AB$	$B+A+9*(8+7+6-5-4)^3-2+1$
9019	15573	$12-3+45*6-7+89AB$	$B+A+9*8*(7-6+5)^4/3/2*1$
901A	15574	$1-(-234-(-5+6))-7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4-3*2)^1$
901B	15575	$-1-(23+45*67)+8*9AB$	$B+A+9-8*(7-6^5/4-3*2)+1$
9020	15576	$1+234-5+6-7-89AB$	$-B*(-A98-7*(6-54+32*-1)))$
9021	15577	$1-23-45*-67+8*9AB$	$-BA9+8+76*54*3-2*-1$
9022	15578	$1-(2-3-(-45*6-(-7-89AB)))$	$B+A+9+8+(-7+6^5+4-3)*2^1$
9023	15579	$1+2+3-4+5^6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8-(-7-6^5+4*3)*2-1$
9024	15580	$123+4+5*6-7*8*9*(A-B)$	$B+A+9-8+7-6^5*(4-3*2)-1$
9025	15581	$-1-2-(3+4*(-5-67)-89AB)$	$B+A+9-8+7-6^5*(4-3*2)^1$
9026	15582	$12*(3+4+5-6-789)*(A-B)$	$BA+9+8*-7*6*(-5+43)-21$
9027	15583	$-1*(234-5-6+7-89AB)$	$-B+A9*87-6+543*(2+1)$
9028	15584	$-1-(-234-5+6-7-89AB)$	$BA-987*(-6-5)-(-43-2)*1$
9029	15585	$1*234+5-(6-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8+7-6^5-4*3)*-2*1$
902A	15586	$1+234+5-6+7+89AB$	$B+A-9-8-7*6+5^4(4*3/2)-1$
902B	15587	$-1*(-234+5-6-7-89AB)$	$-B*(-A-987-6+5*4+3-21)$
9030	15588	$1-(-234-(-5+6-(-7-89AB)))$	$B+A-9-8-7*6+5^4(4*3/2)+1$
9031	15589	$1-2-3^4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+(-7+6^5+4*3)/2+1$
9032	15590	$-12-3*4*5*6-7+89AB$	$B+A9+87*6*(-54+32+1)$
9033	15591	$1+2-3*4+5^6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B-A*987+6*5*(-43-2)*-1$
9034	15592	$-1-23+4*5*(6+7+8)*9A*B$	$BA9+8-7-6*543*(2+1)$
9035	15593	$12-34-(-5*6-7*(8+9)*AB)$	$-B+A987-(6+5*432-1)$
9036	15594	$1^2-3-4+5^6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*7-6+5^4(4*3/2)+1$
9037	15595	$1-2*3*4+5^6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6^5+4*3)*2+1$
9038	15596	$-1+234-(-5-6-7-89AB)$	$B+A*(9+876)+5*(432+1)$
9039	15597	$-1*(234-5-6-7-89AB)$	$-B+A987-6-5*(432-1)$
903A	15598	$1+234-(-5-6-7-89AB)$	$-B+A*9*(87+6+54)-(-32-1)$
903B	15599	$1-2-3+4*5-6*7-8*9-AB$	$-B+A987+6-5*(432+1)$
9040	15600	$1*-2*34*5*(6-(-7+89)+AB)$	$-BA9+8+76*54*3+21$
9041	15601	$-1+234+5*6-7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8*(-7-6^5)/4+3+2^1$
9042	15602	$-1+23-45*6+7+89AB$	$-B-A*-9+(-8765-432)*-1$
9043	15603	$-1-23+4567-8*9*A*B$	$-B-A*-9+8765+432+1$
9044	15604	$12+3*45*(6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5*432*-1$
9045	15605	$1-(2+34)-(-5*6-7-89AB)$	$-B+A987-(-6+5*432)+1$
9046	15606	$-1*23*(45-(6-7*89+A*B))$	$-B-(-A-(987+6*54*(32-1)))$
9047	15607	$1+2-3*4+5^6-7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*5*43*-2-1$
9048	15608	$-1-2*-3-45*-67+8*9AB$	$B-A+987-6*54*(-32+1)$
9049	15609	$1+2+3+45*67-8*9AB$	$B*(-A98-(7+6+5*(-432+1)))$
904A	15610	$1-234*5+6-7-89A*B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7+6^5+4*3)*2+1$
904B	15611	$123-(-4+5-6-7*89*(-A-B))$	$B+A+9-8-(-7-6^5-4*3)*2-1$
9050	15612	$1-2+3-4+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8*(7+6^5/4-3+2)^1$
9051	15613	$12+34-(-5*6+7*(-8-9)*AB)$	$B+A987-(6+5+4)*32+1$
9052	15614	$12-3-(45*6-7+8*9AB)$	$B+A987-(6-5*432*1)$
9053	15615	$-1-(-234+5-6*7-89AB)$	$B+A-9-8-7-6+5^4(4*3/2)-1$
9054	15616	$1-23-4-5*6-7+89AB$	$-BA-987*6-5+4321$
9055	15617	$1-(-234+5+6*-7-89AB)$	$B+A+9*8+(-7+6^5-4-3)*2^1$
9056	15618	$1*2*(-3-45+6-7)*(-8-9A-B)$	$B+A+(9+8+7+6^5-4+3)*2-1$
9057	15619	$1-2-3*4+5^6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-6+5*(-432+1)$
9058	15620	$12-34-5*-67+89AB$	$B*(-A+987-6-5+4+32)*1$
9059	15621	$1+2-3*4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-BA98-(7+654*(-32-1))$
905A	15622	$-1-23+4-(-5*67-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7*6+5^4(4*3/2)+1$
905B	15623	$1+2-3*4+5^6+7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7-(-6^5+4+3)*2-1$
9060	15624	$1*-2*3*4*(567-8-9-AB)$	$B+A+9-(-8*7+(-6^5+4+3)*2*1)$
9061	15625	$1-2*-3*-4*(-567+8+9+AB)$	$B+A987+6-5*432-1$
9062	15626	$12+3*4*(-5*6-7+8*9AB)$	$B-(-A987-6)-5*432*-1$
9063	15627	$1+234-(-5+6*-7)+89AB$	$B+A987+6-5*432+1$
9064	15628	$-1+2*3*(4-(-56+7))+89AB$	$B+A-9-8-7+6+5^4(4*3/2*1)$
9065	15629	$-1-(-23+4*56*-7+89*-AB)$	$B+A-9-8-7+6+5^4(4*3/2)+1$
9066	15630	$-1-23*(-456-(-7-8))-9A*B$	$B+A987-6*5*43*2*-1$
9067	15631	$1+23-(45*6-7-8*9AB)$	$B*(A98+7-6*5*4-(-3+21))$
9068	15632	$12-3*-4*5*6-(-7-89AB)$	$-BA9+8*(765-4+3)*2+1$
9069	15633	$-12-3-(-4+5*6-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5^4(4*3/2)-1$
906A	15634	$1-2*3+4+5*6+7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8-7-6+5^4(4*3/2/1)$
906B	15635	$-1+2+3+4567-8*9*A*B$	$-BA98+7-654*(-32-1)$
9070	15636	$123+4*5*6*-7+89AB$	$B+A+9*8-(-7-6^5+4*3)*2+1$
9071	15637	$-1+234+56-7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8*7-6^5*(4-3*2)-1$
9072	15638	$1+23*4*(-56-78)-9AB$	$B+A+9+8*7+6^5*4^4(3/2-1)$
9073	15639	$1+234+56-(7-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8*7-6^5*(4-3*2)+1$
9074	15640	$-1+2*(-345+67*89)+A+B$	$-B+A9+8765+432-1$
9075	15641	$-1*(-2+3+4-5*67-89AB)$	$-B+A9+8765-432*-1$
9076	15642	$1-2*(345-67*89)+A+B$	$-B+A9+8765+432+1$
9077	15643	$-12+345-67+89AB$	$BA+987*(6+5)+4*(3+21)$
9078	15644	$-1-2-(3*(-45-67)-89AB)$	$B-A-(9*(8+7+6+5+4))^2-1$
9079	15645	$1+2+3*4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B-A+9876+(5-43)*21$
907A	15646	$-1+2+3-4+5*6+7+89AB$	$-B-A987+654*(32-1)$
907B	15647	$12345-6*7*(-89-A*B)$	$-BA9-8*765*(-4+3-2+1)$
9080	15648	$1-(-2-3-(-4-5*6-7))+89AB$	$-BA9+8*-765*(4-3*2)+1$
9081	15649	$1+2*(34+567)+89A*B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6+5+4)^3+2+1$
9082	15650	$1*-2*(-3-4567+8-9+A*-B)$	$B+A+9+8-7-6+5^4(4*3/2/1)$
9083	15651	$-1+234+56+7+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+6^5/(4-3)*2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9084	15652	-1+234-5+67+89AB	B+A+9+8*7+(6^5+4+3)*2^1
9085	15653	1+234-(-56-7-89AB)	-B*(A98-7-65-43+2)*-1
9086	15654	1+234-5+67+89AB	B+A+9-(8-7-6-5*4)^3-2+1
9087	15655	1*-2+345-67+89AB	BA-(9-8765-432+1)
9088	15656	1-(2-345+67)+89AB	BA+9876-5+43*-21
9089	15657	1+2*(3+4567-8-(9-AB))	BA-9+8765-(-432-1)
908A	15658	1*2*(3+4567+8+9A-B)	B+A+9-(8-7-6-5*4)^3+2+1
908B	15659	-12-34+56*7+89AB	-BA-98*(7+6+5-43)+21
9090	15660	1+2+345-67+89AB	B-A+98*(7+6+5+43)-(2-1)
9091	15661	12+3*(45+67)+89AB	BA-9*-87+6*-54*-32*1
9092	15662	-1+234+5+67+89AB	B+A9-(-8765-432)-1
9093	15663	1*234-(-5-67-89AB)	B+A9+8765+432*1
9094	15664	1-(-234-(-5-(-67-89AB)))	B+A9+8765+432+1
9095	15665	1+2*-345*-6-78*(-9A+B)	B+A+9+8+7-6+5^(4*3/2)+1
9096	15666	12*(3+45+67+8+9A-B)	BA+9876+5+43*-21
9097	15667	1+2-3-4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B	B+A+9*8+7+(6^5+4+3)*2+1
9098	15668	-1+23-4-5*-67+89AB	B-A987-654*(-32+1)
9099	15669	1-(2-3456-78*(9A-B))	B+A-9-8*(7-6^5/4-3*2)+1
909A	15670	-1+2*-3*(4+5-67)+89AB	B+A-9-8+7*6+5^(4*3/2)-1
909B	15671	12+345-67+89AB	B+A-9-8+7*6+5^(4*3/2*1)
90A0	15672	-12-(-34-5*67)+89AB	B+A-9-8+7*6+5^(4*3/2)+1
90A1	15673	1+2+3456+78*(9A-B)	BA+9+8765+432-1
90A2	15674	1-2+3*(-4+567-89A)*-B	BA+9+8765-432*-1
90A3	15675	1234-5+(-6-(-7+89))*-AB	BA+9+8765+432+1
90A4	15676	1-(-2+34)-(-56*7-89AB)	B+A+9+8+7+6+5^(4*3/2*1)
90A5	15677	1-2+3+4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B	B+A+9+8+7+6+5^(4*3/2)+1
90A6	15678	1+2+3*(-4+567-89A)*-B	B+A+9+8*(7+6^5/4+3+2)^1
90A7	15679	1*2-3*4+5^6+7*8+9+A-B	B+A+9+(8*7+6^5-4-3)*2-1
90A8	15680	12*(3+4-5+6-(-789-(A-B)))	B+A+9+(-8-7+6^5+4+3)*2^1
90A9	15681	-1-(23+4-56*7-89AB)	B+A+(-9-8+7+6^5+4+3)*2^1
90AA	15682	1-2+3*4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B	B+A*987+6-(-54-3)*21
90AB	15683	-1-2+34-(-5*-67-89AB)	B+A+9*8+(-7-6^5-4*3)*-2/1
90B0	15684	12+3456-78*(-9A+B)	B+A+9*8+(7+6^5+4*3)*2+1
90B1	15685	-1+23+4+56-7*(8+9)*-AB	B+A+(-9+8-7+6^5+4+3)*2/1
90B2	15686	-1*-2*(34+567-(8+9A))*B	-B*(A-987-(6+5+4)-(-3+21))
90B3	15687	12-34+56*7+89AB	B+A-9+8+7*6+5^(4*3/2*1)
90B4	15688	-1*-2*(3+4567+8-9+AB)	-B-A98-76*54*-3-21
90B5	15689	-1-23+4+56*7+89AB	B+A+9-8+7*6+5^(4*3/2*1)
90B6	15690	1*(-23-(-456+78))* (9A+B)	B+A+9-8+7*6+5^(4*3/2)+1
90B7	15691	-1-2-34*-5*67-89A+B	B+A-9+(-8+7+6^5+4+3)*2+1
90B8	15692	-1*-2*(3-(-4567-(-8+9)))+AB	-B-A9*(8-7*6)+5432-1
90B9	15693	1-2+345+6*-7+89AB	B+A+9+(8*7+6^5)^(-4-3)*2-1
90BA	15694	1-(2-34)-(-56+7*(8+9))*-AB	BA9+87-6*543*(-2-1)
90BB	15695	-1-(-2-345)+6*-7+89AB	B+A+9-8-7+(-6^5-4+3)*-2/1
9100	15696	1*-2*3*-4*(-5+6*78-(-9A+B))	B+A+9+(-8*-7+6^5+4-3)*2/1
9101	15697	1+2+345-6*7+89AB	B*(A-98*7-(6+5+432))*-1
9102	15698	1+234-56+7*-89*(-A-B)	B+A-9+8*7+6+5^(4*3/2)-1
9103	15699	1+2+3+4+5^6-7+8*9+A-B	B+A+9*(8*7*6*5+4+3-2)^1
9104	15700	-12-3+4+56*7+89AB	B+A-9+8*7+6+5^(4*3/2)+1
9105	15701	1-2+3-4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B	B+A+9*(8-7)*6+5^(4*3/2)+1
9106	15702	-1*2*(3-(-4567+8+9A)-B)	B+A+(-9-8*7-6^5+4-3)*-2+1
9107	15703	1-2-3+4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B	B+A+((9-8)^7+6^5+4+3)*2^1
9108	15704	12345-(6-7*(-89A-B))	B+A+9+8+7*6+5^(4*3/2)-1
9109	15705	1-(2+3+4)-(-56*7-89AB)	B+A+9+8+7*6+5^(4*3/2*1)
910A	15706	-12+3+4-56*7+89AB	B+A+9+8+7*6+5^(4*3/2)+1
910B	15707	1+2-3+4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B	B+A+(-9*-8+7+6^5-4*3)*2^1
9110	15708	-12*(-3+4-(-5-67)-(-8-(9A+B)))*-B	B*(A+9-87)*(-6+54-3*21)
9111	15709	-12+345-6-7+89AB	B+A+9+(-8+7+6^5+4+3)*2+1
9112	15710	1*-2*(3-4567+8*(-9A)+B)	B+A+9+8*(7+6^5/4+3+2)^1
9113	15711	1^2+3+4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B	B+A+9+8*7+(6-5+4)^(3*2)/1
9114	15712	1*(2-3*4-5*6)*(-789+AB)	-B-A98+76*54*3-2+1
9115	15713	1-2-3+4+56*7+89AB	-B-A98-76*-54*3*(2-1)
9116	15714	1*23*(-4*-5*67-8+9*-A*B)	-B-A+9*-8*-76+5432+1
9117	15715	-123+456-(7-89AB)	B+A+((-9+8)*-7+6^5+4+3)*2*1
9118	15716	12345+6-7*(89A+B)	B+A+9+8*7+6+5^(4*3/2)-1
9119	15717	-1-2+3+4+56*7+89AB	B+A+9+8*7+6+5^(4*3/2/1)
911A	15718	-1*-2*(34-567*-8+9AB)	B+A+9+8*7+6+5^(4*3/2)+1
911B	15719	1*(-23-45-67-89A)*-B	-B*(-A9-(876+5)-43+2*-1)
9120	15720	-1-2+345-6-7+89AB	BA98+7*(-65-432-1)
9121	15721	-1-(234-567-89AB)	B+A-9-((-8-(7+6^5+4+3))*2+1)
9122	15722	1-2+345-6-(7-89AB)	BA98-7*6+54*3*-21
9123	15723	-12+345-(6-7)+89AB	B-A9*(8-76)+5*-432*-1
9124	15724	-1+2+345-6-(7-89AB)	B+A+9+8+7-(-6^5-4+3)*2-1
9125	15725	-1*(-2-(345-6-7+89AB))	-BA+9*(876+54+321)
9126	15726	1+2+345-6-(7-89AB)	B+A+9*8+7+(6-5+4)^(3*2)+1
9127	15727	1234-(5+67)-89*-AB	BA98-7*(65+432)*1
9128	15728	12-(3-4-56*7-89AB)	-B-A*-9*(87+65)-(-4+321)
9129	15729	-123+456+7+89AB	B+A+9*8*7/6+5^(4*3/2)-1
912A	15730	1-23-4*(-5*-6*-78-9*AB)	-B*(-A-(987-6+54-32+1))
912B	15731	1*2+3+4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B	B+A+9*8+7+6+5^(4*3/2^1)
9130	15732	-1-2+345-(-6+7)+89AB	-B+A+9*8*76+5432-1
9131	15733	123-45*-6-7+89AB	B-A98-76*54*-3+2*-1
9132	15734	12-(-3-4+56*-7-89AB)	-B-(-A-9*-8*7*-6*5-(432+1))
9133	15735	-12+345+6+7+89AB	B-(A98+76*54*3*(-2+1))
9134	15736	-1+2-(-345-6)-7+89AB	B+A9*87+6+54*32*1
9135	15737	12-(-345+6+7-89AB)	-B-A+987*6-5+4321
9136	15738	1+2+345-(-6+7-89AB)	-B-(A98-76*54*3-21)
9137	15739	-12+34+56*7+89AB	B+A+(-9*8-7-6^5-4)/(-3/2+1)
9138	15740	1+2+345-6-(-7-89AB)	B+A+9+(-8-7-6^5-4+3)*-2^1
9139	15741	-1+2+3-45*-67+89*-A*-B	B*(A9+876+54-3-2+1)
913A	15742	-1+2-34*-5*67+8*9-AB	-B*-A+9-(8-7-6-5*4)^3-2/1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
913B	15743	$-1+234*(-56-7-8-(-9A-B))$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7*6)*-5+4)*(-3*2-1)$
9140	15744	$-1*2*3*4*(-5-(6*(7+89))-(A+B))$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*6^5+4+3)*2-1$
9141	15745	$-12+3456-7*(8-9AB)$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*6^5+4+3)*2^1$
9142	15746	$-1-23-4*56*7*-8-9*-A*B$	$B+A+(9*8+7+6^5+4+3)*2+1$
9143	15747	$123-45*-6+7+89AB$	$-B-A+9*8*(7*6^5+4+3+2)^1$
9144	15748	$1-(2-345-6-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9+8*7-(-6^5-4^3)*2/1$
9145	15749	$12+345+6-7+89AB$	$BA+987-6*54*(-32+1)$
9146	15750	$-1-(-2-345-6)+7+89AB$	$B+A-((-9-8-(7-(-6^5-4^3))))*2-1)$
9147	15751	$12+345-(6-(7+89AB))$	$BA98-(7+6+54*-3*-21)$
9148	15752	$1+2-(-345-(6+7)-89AB)$	$-B*(A-987-65-4+32)*1$
9149	15753	$1^2+3^4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*6)*(-5-4^3)*-2*1$
914A	15754	$-1+2345-(-678-9A)*B$	$-B-A*9*(-87-(65-4))+3*-21$
914B	15755	$-1*(23-4)*(-567-8-9+AB)$	$-B-A-98*(7-6-5)*(-4+32^1)$
9150	15756	$1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9AB$	$B+A-9*8*-76-(-5432-1)$
9151	15757	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+(9-8*7+6-5)*(-4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
9152	15758	$1*2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A-9*8*(6-5+4-(-3+21))$
9153	15759	$-12+34*5*(-6+78)-9AB$	$B-A+987*6-5+4321$
9154	15760	$-12-34*-5*67+89-AB$	$B-A98-76*54*3+21$
9155	15761	$-1+2*3^4+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B-A*9+(-87-65)*4*(3-21)$
9156	15762	$1234-56+7+89*AB$	$BA*(9+87-(65-43)+21)$
9157	15763	$12+345-(-6-(7+89AB))$	$-B*(-A-9+87*-6-543-21)$
9158	15764	$-12*(-34-(-5-6*7*8)-9AB)$	$-B-A-9*(8-(-7*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2)-1$
9159	15765	$-1-23*(4-5)*-6*7*-8-9A*B$	$BA98+7-6-54*3*21$
915A	15766	$(-1+2)*3+4+5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9*(87-(6-543))*-2*-1$
915B	15767	$12+34-56*-7+89AB$	$-B+A+987*6+5+4321$
9160	15768	$-1*2+3^4+5^6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8*7+6)*-5*(-4-3)-2-1$
9161	15769	$1-2+3^4+5^6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7-6)*-5*(4+3)-2/1$
9162	15770	$12345-6-7*89A-B$	$B+A-9*(8*7+6)*-5*(-4-3)-2+1$
9163	15771	$-1*(23+4-567-(-8-9))*(A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7*6)*(5^4-(-3-2)*1)$
9164	15772	$-1*-2*(34+5-67-8*9*-A*B)$	$-B-A9-8*(7-(-6+54))*32+1$
9165	15773	$12+3456-7*(8-9AB)$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7-6)*-5*(4+3)+2/1$
9166	15774	$1234+5+6*-7+89*AB$	$-B*(A-987-(6+5-4+32^1))$
9167	15775	$-1-2-(-345-6*7)+89AB$	$B+A-9*(-8-7)-(6-5^{\wedge}(-4*-3/2))^1$
9168	15776	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(7+6^5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
9169	15777	$1+2*3^4+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*(4+3)*21$
916A	15778	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A9*-87+6-54*(-32-1)$
916B	15779	$1+2*3^4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B-(-A-987*6+5-4321)$
9170	15780	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7-8+9+A-B$	$-B+A-98-7*(-6-5*(-4+321))$
9171	15781	$1+2-(-345-6*7-89AB)$	$BA98-7+6*(-543-21)$
9172	15782	$123+4*-5*(6-78)*9+AB$	$-B-A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4+3)*2-1$
9173	15783	$1-2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(9*8*7+6^5+4)/(-3-2+1)$
9174	15784	$1^2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4+3)*2+1$
9175	15785	$1^2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B*(-A+9)*(87+65*-4)*(3*2+1)$
9176	15786	$-12-34*5*-67-(8-9-A+B)$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5-4^3)*2-1$
9177	15787	$1+2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+(-7-6^5-4^3)*-2*1$
9178	15788	$1+2*3^4+5^6-(-7-8)^9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8-(-7-(6^5+4^3))^*2+1$
9179	15789	$-1-2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A+B$	$B+A+987*6+5+4321$
917A	15790	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3+4+5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA-9+87*(-6+5)*4*-32+1$
917B	15791	$12345+6*7*(8-(-9+AB))$	$-B-A-9*(8+7+6)+(-5*-4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$
9180	15792	$1*(-23+4-5)*(6*-78+9-A-B)$	$-B-A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4^3)*2-1$
9181	15793	$1234-5-6-7-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*6+(-5*4)^{\wedge}3)*-2/1$
9182	15794	$1-2+34*-5*-67+89-A*B$	$B+A-9+(-8-7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
9183	15795	$1+2*3^4+5^6+7-8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6*(543+21)$
9184	15796	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7+8+9+A-B$	$-B*(-A98-7+65-(-43+2-1))$
9185	15797	$-1-2+34*5*-67-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8+7*6)*(5^4+3*2)+1$
9186	15798	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5-(4+3))^*2+1$
9187	15799	$1*2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8*7+6-5)*(-4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
9188	15800	$1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A9*87+6-54*(-32-1)$
9189	15801	$-12+345+67+89AB$	$BA-98*(-7-65-43)-(-2-1)$
918A	15802	$123+456+78*-9*A*-B$	$-B-A+(-9*(-8-7)+6^5)/(-4-3)*2+1$
918B	15803	$1234-(-5+6-(-7+89*AB))$	$B+A+(9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
9190	15804	$12345+6+7*-89A+B$	$B+A-9-(-8*-7+6^5+4^3)*-2*1$
9191	15805	$1234-(-5+6+7-89*AB)$	$B+A+((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
9192	15806	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)-5*6*7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A*987-6+5-4*-321$
9193	15807	$1234-5-(-6-7-89*AB)$	$B*(A+987+65-43+2*1)$
9194	15808	$1*2+3^4+5^6+7+8*9+A+B$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5-(4-3))^*2-1$
9195	15809	$12+34*5*6*7+89+A*B$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5-(4-3))^*2^1$
9196	15810	$1*-2*(3-4567-8-9*(A+B))$	$B+A+(9/-8-7)*-6^5/4-3*2^1$
9197	15811	$1-2*(-3+4-56-7*-8*(-9-AB))$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5)*(-4+3*2)*1$
9198	15812	$-1-2-(-345-67-89AB)$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
9199	15813	$123-(4-5*67)+89AB$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2^1)$
919A	15814	$1-2+345+67+89AB$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6)^5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
919B	15815	$1234-(-5-(-6-7)+89*-AB)$	$-B-A*98*(-7-6)+543-21$
91A0	15816	$-1+2+345+67+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8*7)/-6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*2^1$
91A1	15817	$1*2+345+67+89AB$	$B+A+(9/-8-7)*-6^5/4+3-2/1$
91A2	15818	$1+2-(-345-67)+89AB$	$-B*(-A98-7-(-65-43+2)-1)$
91A3	15819	$1234-5+6+7-89*-AB$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4)*3(-2-1)$
91A4	15820	$1-2-(-3+4*-56*7-89A*B)$	$B+A+(-9/-8+7)*6^5/4+3+2-1$
91A5	15821	$(-1-(2-3^4-5*-6*-7*8))^9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(65-4)*32+1$
91A6	15822	$1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7*8-9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9/-8+7)*6^5/4+3+2+1$
91A7	15823	$(1-2-3)^{\wedge}4+5^6+7-8*9+A+B$	$B+A+9+(-8*-7+6^5+4^3)*2+1$
91A8	15824	$-12-34*-5*67+8-(-9-A-B)$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4+3)*2-1$
91A9	15825	$1-2+34*5*67-(89-AB)$	$BA9+8*7*6*(54+3-21)$
91AA	15826	$1*2+3^4+5^6+7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+((-9-8)*-7+6^5+4+3)*2+1$
91AB	15827	$1-23+4*56+7*(8+9)*AB$	$-B*-A+((-9-8)*-7*(-6-5)*-4+3)*(2+1)$
91B0	15828	$-1+234+56+7*89*(A+B)$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7)-(-6^5+4+3))^*2-1$
91B1	15829	$12-(-345-67)+89AB$	$-B-A*9*(-87+6*54-321)$
91B2	15830	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A*9*(-87-65+4)+3-2*1$
91B3	15831	$1*2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7-6^5-4^3)*-2/1$
91B4	15832	$123+4*5*(67+8)*9-A+B$	$B+A-9*(8+7+6)+(-5*-4)^{\wedge}3*2^1$
91B5	15833	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7+6)+(-5*-4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
91B6	15834	$-12 * (-34 - 5 - (-6 + 789 - A - B))$	$B + A + ((-9 - 8) * -7 + 6^5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1$
91B7	15835	$12 + 3 + 4 * 56 * 7 - 89A * -B$	$B + A + ((-9 - 8) * -7 + 6^5 + 4^3) * 2^1$
91B8	15836	$1 + 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 * 8 - 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA - 9 * -876 - 54 * -3 * 2^1$
91B9	15837	$-1 - 2 + 34 * (-5 - 6 + 7) * (-8 + 9 - A) * B$	$-B + A * -9 - (87 - 65) * (-432 + 1)$
91BA	15838	$-1 * 2 + 3^4 + 5^6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + (-9 - 8 * 7 - 6 - (-5 * 4)^3) * 2 + 1$
91BB	15839	$(-1 * -2 - 3 * 4 - 5 * 6 * 7) * -8 * 9 + A - B$	$-BA - 9 + (87 - 65) * (432 + 1)$
9200	15840	$-1 * (234 - 5 - 6 - (-789 - A)) * -B$	$B * (A9 - 87 + 6 + 54 * (-3 + 21))$
9201	15841	$1 - 2 * (34 + 5) * (6 - 7 * (-89 + AB))$	$BA9 + 87 - (6 + 5) * -43 * 2^1$
9202	15842	$1 * 2 + 3^4 + 5^6 + (7 + 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B - A * (98 - (765 + 432)) + 1$
9203	15843	$1 + 2 + 3^4 + 5^6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-B + A - 98 + 7 * -6 * -5 * (43 + 21)$
9204	15844	$-1 * 2 * (3456 + 7 + 89 * -AB)$	$B + A + (-9 * (-8 - 7) + 6^5) / (4 - 3) * 2 + 1$
9205	15845	$1 * 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 * 9 - (A + B)$	$B - A - 98 - 7 * 6 * -5 * (43 + 21)$
9206	15846	$((1 + 2)^(3 + 4) - 5 * 6 * 7) * 8 + 9 + A + B$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + 7 * 6) * (5^4 + 3^2 - 1)$
9207	15847	$(-1 + 2 + 3^4 - 4) * (5^6 + 7 - (8 - 9)) + A + B$	$-B - A - 9 + (8 - 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^3) ^2 + 1$
9208	15848	$1234 - 5 + 6 * 7 - 89 * -AB$	$B + A + (-9 - 8) * -7 * ((-6 - 5) * -4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$
9209	15849	$-1 * -2 * (-3 - 4 * 5) * (-6 * 7 * 8 - 9) - (A + B)$	$-BA + 987 + 6 * -54 * -32 * 1$
920A	15850	$1 - 23 - 4 * (-5 - (67 + 89)) * (A + B)$	$-BA + 987 - 6 * 54 * -32 + 1$
920B	15851	$123 - 4 * 5 * (-6 - 78) * (9 - (-A + B))$	$B * (-A + 987 - (-6 - 5 - 4) + 32 - 1)$
9210	15852	$12 + 34 * 5 * 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 - A - B$	$B + A - 9 * (8 * 7 + 6) + 5 + 4^3 (3 * 2 + 1)$
9211	15853	$1 * 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 * 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$-B - A - 9 + 8 + (-7 - 6^4 - (5 + 4)^3) ^2 - 1$
9212	15854	$1 + 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 - 7 + 8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA98 + 76 + 54 * 3 * -21$
9213	15855	$1 * 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 * 8 - 9 + A + B$	$B + A + 9 + (8 + 7) * (6 * 5 + 4^3 (3 + 2) + 1)$
9214	15856	$1 - 2 * (-3 - 4) - (56 + 7) * (-8 + (-9 - A) * B)$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 - 21$
9215	15857	$-12 + 3456 + 7 * (8 + 9AB)$	$B + A + (-9 * (-8 - 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3) * 2^1$
9216	15858	$-1 - 23 + 456 + 7 + 89AB$	$B + A + (-9 * -8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1$
9217	15859	$-12 - 3 * (-456 - (-789 - A)) * -B$	$-B + A987 + 654 * -3 - 21$
9218	15860	$1 - 23 - (-456 + 7) + 89AB$	$B + A + (-9 * -8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4^3) * 2 + 1$
9219	15861	$1 + 234 + (5 + 6) * (-7 - 8 + 9AB)$	$B + A + 9 * 8 * (7 * 6 * 5 + 4 * 3 - 2) ^1$
921A	15862	$-12 * (3 + 4 + 56 + 78 + 9A * -B)$	$B * (-A + 987 * (6 - 5) + 43 - 2 * -1)$
921B	15863	$-1 - 23 * (-456 + 7) - 89A - B$	$-B - A + 9 + (8 - 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^3) ^2 - 1$
9220	15864	$-1 + 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 * 8 - (-7 * -6 + (-5 * 4)^3) * 2 - 1$
9221	15865	$1 * 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A9 * 8 * 7 + 65 * -4 * -3 * 2^1$
9222	15866	$1 + 2 * 3^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A9 * -87 + (-6 - 54) * (-32 + 1)$
9223	15867	$(1 + 2) ^3 * 4 + 5^6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9 * 8 * (7 - 65 - 4) * -3 + 21$
9224	15868	$-1 - 2 + 3456 + 7 * (8 + 9AB)$	$B - A + 9 * (876 + 54 + 321)$
9225	15869	$-12 - 3 - (-456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$-B - A - 9 + (-8 - 7 * 6) * (-5 * 4^3 + 2) - 1$
9226	15870	$-1 + 2 + 34 * 5 * (-6 - 7 + 8 - 9) - AB$	$B + A + (-9 - (8 - 7 * 6)) * (5^4 + 3^2 - 1)$
9227	15871	$-12 + 34 + 5 - 6 * (-7 - (8 + 9)) * -A * -B$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * 7 - 6 * 5 + 4^3 (3 * 2 + 1)$
9228	15872	$-1 - 23 + 456 - (-7 - 89AB)$	$-B + A987 + 6 * (-5 - 4 - 321)$
9229	15873	$1 + 2 * (-3456 - (-7 + 89 * -AB))$	$B * (A + 987 + 65 - 4 - 32 - 1)$
922A	15874	$1 - 23 - (-456 - 7) + 89AB$	$B + A - 9 * 8 + (7 + 6) * (-5 * (4 + 3)) ^2 + 1$
922B	15875	$-123 - 4 - (-567 - 89AB)$	$BA + 9 * 8 * 76 - (-5432 + 1)$
9230	15876	$-1 * 23 * -4 * (-5 - 6) * -7 * (8 - 9) * (-A - B)$	$B + A + (-9 * 8 * ((-7 + 6) * 5 * -4)^3) * 2 - 1$
9231	15877	$(-1 + 2 - 3 / 4 + 5) * -6 * -7 * 8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * 7 * (6 - (-5 * 4 + 3)^2) - 1$
9232	15878	$1234 - 5 - (6 + 7 - 89A) * B$	$-BA - (-9876 + 543 + 2 + 1)$
9233	15879	$(1^2 + 3) ^4 + 5^6 + (7 - 8) ^9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 - 2 * 1$
9234	15880	$1234 - (-56 + 7) - 89 * -AB$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 - 2 + 1$
9235	15881	$1 + 2 * -3 + 456 - (7 - 89AB)$	$-BA - (-9876 + 543 * (2 - 1))$
9236	15882	$1 - 2 - (3 - 456 - (-7 + 89AB))$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 + 2 - 1$
9237	15883	$-123 + 4 - (-567 - 89AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 - 2 * -1$
9238	15884	$-1 + 2 - 3 + 456 - 7 + 89AB$	$-B + A987 + 654 * 3 * (-2 + 1)$
9239	15885	$1234 - 5 - (-67 - 89 * AB)$	$B + A - 9 * -8 * ((-7 * -6 + 5^4) / 3 - 2^1)$
9240	15886	$-1 - (2 - 3 - 456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$-B - (-A987 + 654 * 3) + 2 * 1$
9241	15887	$-1 * (2 - 3 - 456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$-B + A987 - 654 * 3 + 2 + 1$
9242	15888	$123 + 4 - (-56 * 7 - 89AB)$	$B + A - 9 + (8 - 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^3) ^2 + 1$
9243	15889	$-12 + 3 + 456 + 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - 9 + (8 - 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^3) ^2 + 1$
9244	15890	$-1 - (-2 - 3) - (-456 + 7) + 89AB$	$-BA - (-9876 + 5 * 4^3 + 32 + 1)$
9245	15891	$-1 + 2 * 3 - (-456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 * 4 * 32 * 1$
9246	15892	$-12 + 34 * 5 * 67 - (-89 - (-A + B))$	$-B + A987 + (-65 + 4) * 32 - 1$
9247	15893	$1 - 23 * -456 - (7 + 8 + 9AB)$	$B + A987 - 6 * (5 + 4 + 321)$
9248	15894	$1234 + 56 + 7 + 89 * AB$	$B * (A98 - 76 + 5 - 43 + 21)$
9249	15895	$1234 + 5 + 67 - 89 * -AB$	$B + A + (9 * 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4 + 3) ^2 - 1$
924A	15896	$1 - 2 - (3 - 456 - 7 - 89AB)$	$B + A + (9 * 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4 + 3) ^2 * 1$
924B	15897	$-1 + 2 - 3 + 456 - (-7 - 89AB)$	$-BA - (9 + 8 * -765 - 4321)$
924C	15898	$-12 + 3 + 456 * 7 + 8 * 9AB$	$B + A - 9 + (7 * 6^4 - (5 - 4) * 3) ^2 + 1$
924D	15899	$1 + 2 - 3 + 456 + 7 + 89AB$	$BA - 987 * -6 - (5 - 4321)$
9250	15900	$-1 * (2 - 3 - (456 - (-7 - 89AB)))$	$B + A + 9 * 8 * 7 / (-6 + 5) + 4^3 (3 * 2 + 1)$
9251	15901	$1 - 2 + 3 + 456 + 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * 7 + 6 - 5 + 4^3 (3 * 2 + 1)$
9252	15902	$12 + 3 - (-456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$B + A + (9 * -8 + 7 + 6 - (-5 * 4)^3) * 2 * 1$
9253	15903	$-12 * (3 - 456 - 789 + A + B)$	$BA * (9 + 87) * (65 - 43 - 21)$
9254	15904	$-1 - 23 * -456 - (-7 + 8 + 9AB)$	$B + A987 - 654 * 3 - 2 + 1$
9255	15905	$-123 + 456 + 7 * -89 * (-A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - (543 - 21)$
9256	15906	$1 + 2 * 3 - (-456 - 7) + 89AB$	$B + A + 9 + (8 - 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^3) ^2 + 1$
9257	15907	$123 - 45 * -67 + 89 * A * B$	$B + A987 + 654 * -3 + 2 * 1$
9258	15908	$-1 * 2 + (-3 + 4 * 5) * (-6 - 7) * -8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A9 + 8 * 765 + 4321$
9259	15909	$-1 + (2^3 + 4 + 5) * (-6 - 7) * 8 * -9 + A - B$	$BA + 987 * 6 + 5 + 4321$
925A	15910	$12 - 3 + 456 + 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - 9 + (-8 - 7 * 6) * (-5 * 4^3 + 2) - 1$
925B	15911	$-1 + 23 - (-456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
925C	15912	$1 + 2 * -3 * (-4 + 5 * 6) * (-78 - 9 + A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * (7 * 6^4 - (5 - 4) * 3) ^2 - 1$
925D	15913	$1 + 23 - (-456 + 7 - 89AB)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * (7 * 6^4 - (5 - 4) * 3) ^2 * 1$
9260	15914	$1 * 2 + (-3 + 4 * 5) * (-6 - 7) * -8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A987 + (-654 + 3) * (2 + 1)$
9261	15915	$1 + 2 + (-3 + 4 * 5) * (-6 - 7) * -8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA - 9 - 8 * -765 + 4321$
9262	15916	$12 + 3 - (-456 - 7 - 89AB)$	$-BA - 9 - 87 * -6 * (54 - 32) * 1$
9263	15917	$-1 + 2 - 3 * (-456 - 7) - 89A * -B$	$-B - A + (-9 - 8 + 7) * 6 + (-5 * -4)^3 * 2 - 1$
9264	15918	$12 + 34 * 5 * 67 + 89 * (-A + B)$	$B + A - (9 + 8 + (-7 * -6 + (-5 * 4)^3) * 2 + 1)$
9265	15919	$-123 + 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 89AB$	$BA98 - (-7 + 6 * 543 + 21)$
9266	15920	$12 - 3 - 456 * -7 - 8 * -9AB$	$B + A - 9 + (-8 - 7) * 6 + (-5 * -4)^3 * 2 - 1$
9267	15921	$1 - (-2 * 3^4 - (5^6 - (-7 - 8) * 9)) + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + (-8 - 7) * 6 + (-5 * -4)^3 * 2^1$
9268	15922	$-1 - 2 + 34 * -5 * -67 + 89 + A + B$	$B + A + 9 * -8 + (-7 - 6 - (-5 * 4)^3) * 2^1$
9269	15923	$12 - 34 * 5 * -67 - (8 - 9) * -A * -B$	$B + A + ((-9 + 8 + 7) * -6 + 5^4) / 3^4 (-2 - 1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9271	15925	$1+(2+3^4(4-5+6))^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-7-6^*(543+2-1)$
9272	15926	$-1+23+456+7+89AB$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7-6^*-5^*(-4^3-2^*1))$
9273	15927	$1+2-3^*4^*(56-7-(8+9A)*B)$	$B+A+9-(-8^*(7-6^*-5^*(4^3+2)))-1$
9274	15928	$1+23+456+7+89AB$	$BA98-7-6^*543-2-1$
9275	15929	$1-2+34^*-5^*-67+8-9+AB$	$B+A+9+(-8-7^*6)^*(-5^*4^3+2)-1$
9276	15930	$-1^*2^*(34-5)^*(6+78+9^*A-B)$	$B+A+9+(-8-7^*6)^*(-5^*4^3+2)^*1$
9277	15931	$(-1+2/3+4^*5)^*-6^*(-7-8)^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98+7-654^*(-3-2)^*-1$
9278	15932	$-12^*(34+56-(789+AB))$	$BA98+7+6^*(-543-2)-1$
9279	15933	$(-1^*(2^3+4)-5)^*(-6-7)^*-8^*-9+A+B$	$BA98+7+6^*(-543+2^*-1)$
927A	15934	$-1+(-2^*3+4)^5*(6+7^*-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*-543+2+1$
927B	15935	$1-23^*4+5-67^*(-8^*9-AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8-7^*6-(-5^*4)^3)^*2^1$
9280	15936	$-1+23^*(4+56)+(7+89A)*B$	$B+A-9^*8-7-6+(-5^*-4)^3^*2^1$
9281	15937	$(-1^*2^*3+4)^5*(6-7^*8^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B+A9^*87-(-6-54)^*32+1$
9282	15938	$(-1-(2+(-3-4^*5)^*(-6-7)^*8))^*-9+A-B$	$B+A+((-9-8)^*-7+6^5+4^3)^*2-1$
9283	15939	$-1^*(234-5+6+(-7-89)^*-A)^*-B$	$B^*(-A-987+6+5-43)^*(-2+1)$
9284	15940	$1-2^*-3^*(-4+(-5+6^*7)^*8^*9)-(A+B)$	$B+A+((-9-8)^*-7+6^5+4^3)^*2+1$
9285	15941	$-1-23^*4+567+89AB$	$B-A^*-9-(87+65)^*-4^*(-3+21)$
9286	15942	$12345-678^*9-AB$	$BA98+7-(-6^*-543+2)-1$
9287	15943	$1+23^*-4+567+89AB$	$BA+98^*(76-5+43)+21$
9288	15944	$1-(-2^*3^4-5^6-(-7-8)^*9))+A+B$	$BA98+7-6^*543-(2-1)$
9289	15945	$-1^*(2+3)^*(45^*-67-(-8-9^*A^*B))$	$BA98+7+6^*-543^*(2-1)$
928A	15946	$-12^*(3-45-(6+78-9+A)*B)$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6)^*(-5^*(4+3))^2-1$
928B	15947	$(-1/-2+3^*-4-5^*-6^*-7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-6^*-543-2^*1)$
9290	15948	$-1-(2-3^4-(5^6-(-7-8)^*9))+A^*B$	$B+A987-6^*(5-4)^*321$
9291	15949	$(1-2-3)^4+5^6+7^*8-9+A+B$	$BA98-7-6^*(543-2-1)$
9292	15950	$1^*(234-(-5+6)-(-789-A))^*B$	$B-A9-87^*6^*(-54-32^*-1)$
9293	15951	$(-1+2/3+4^*5)^*-6^*(-7-8)^*9+A+B$	$B+A-9^*8+7-(6-(-5^*-4)^3^*2-1)$
9294	15952	$1234+5-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*8-(-7+6+(-5^*4)^3)^*2+1$
9295	15953	$1^*2+3^4+5^6+7+8)^*9+A^*B$	$B+A+9+8-(-7^*-6+(-5^*4)^3)^*2-1$
9296	15954	$(-1-(-2^3-(4-5^*6^*7)^*8)^*9-(A+B)$	$B+A+9+8+(-7^*-6+(-5^*4)^3)^*2^*1$
9297	15955	$1-23-45^*6^*-7-89^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8-(-7^*-6+(-5^*4)^3)^*2+1$
9298	15956	$(-1-(2-(-3^*-4-5^*6^*7)^*8))^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*-543+21$
9299	15957	$-1^*-23^*(-45-67^*-8-9+A+B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7+6)^*(5-4^*3^2-1)$
929A	15958	$1+(-2^*3+4)^5*(6+7^*-8^*9)+A+B$	$B+A-9^*(8-7+6)+(-5^*-4)^3^*2^*1$
929B	15959	$1+23^*(456-7)-8+9^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(8-(7-6))+(-5^*-4)^3^*2+1$
92A0	15960	$-1-2-34^*-5^*67-8^*(-9-A)+B$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)^*6+(-5^*-4)^3^*2-1$
92A1	15961	$(1^2+3)^4+5^6+7+8^*9-(A-B)$	$B^*(A+987-6+5+4+32+1)$
92A2	15962	$1-(-2-3^*4^*(56-7+89A))+B$	$B+A-9+(-8-7^*6)^*(-5^*4^3+2-1)$
92A3	15963	$1234-56-7+89A^*B$	$BA98+7-6^*(543-2-1)$
92A4	15964	$((1+2)^3+3+4)^*(5+6-7^*-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6)^*(-5^*(4+3))^2+1$
92A5	15965	$-1-2^*3^4+5^6+7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9+8-7-6+(-5^*-4)^3^*2^*1$
92A6	15966	$-1+2^*34^*-5+(-6-7)^*(-89A+B)$	$B+A-9/(8-7)^*6+(-5^*-4)^3^*2-1$
92A7	15967	$1-2^*3^4+5^6+7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA9-8^*(-76+5)^*(43-21)$
92A8	15968	$-1/-2^*(3^*4^5+6^7/8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8^*7-6+(5^*4)^3^*2^1$
92A9	15969	$-1-2^*34-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A+9^*8+(7^*6^5(5-4)^3)^2^*1$
92AA	15970	$1-2^*(-3-4^*5^*6)^*(7^*8+9)-(A+B)$	$-B-A+987-6^*-54^*32^*1$
92AB	15971	$1+23^*4-(-5-6)^*(7+8+9AB)$	$B+A^*(98-76-5)^*(43+21)$
92B0	15972	$-1^*(-234+5-6-(789+A))^*B$	$-B^*(-A-987-65-4+32)^*1$
92B1	15973	$12+3^*4^*(56-7)+89AB$	$B+A-9+8^*7^*6+5^5(4+3-2+1)$
92B2	15974	$12^*(34+5-(-678-9-AB))$	$B+A-9+8^*7^*6+5^5(4^3/2)+1$
92B3	15975	$1+234+5^*67+89AB$	$B+A-9^*8+(-7-6+(-5^*4)^3)^*-2/1$
92B4	15976	$-1^*-2^*(-345-678^*-9-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8-7^*6^*5^*(-43-21)$
92B5	15977	$1-2-3-45^*-6^*7+89^*AB$	$-B-A+9876-543-21$
92B6	15978	$(-1-(2-(-3^*-4-5^*6^*7)^*8))^*9+A+B$	$B+A-9+8-7^*6+(-5^*-4)^3^*2/1$
92B7	15979	$(-1+2^*3)^*-4^*(-5-6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-876+54^*-3^*-2^*1$
92B8	15980	$(1-(2+3)^4)^*-5^*(6-7/8)-9+A-B$	$-B-A9-8-7^*6^*54^*-3^*2^*1$
92B9	15981	$-12+34^*56+789A-B$	$-B-A-987^*(-6-5)+432-1$
92BA	15982	$-1^*(-2-34-(-56+7)+89)^*-AB$	$-B+A9^*8-(-76+543)^*-21$
92BB	15983	$-1+2-34^*-5^*67-8^*-9+A^*B$	$B^*(A+987-(-6-(-5-4+32)))-1$
9300	15984	$1^*-23^*(45+6+7+8)^*(-9-A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-(8+7-6+(-5^*4)^3))^*2-1$
9301	15985	$1^*2+(-3^*-4-5^*6^*7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*8^*7/6^*5+4^3(3^*2+1)$
9302	15986	$1+2+(-3^*-4-5^*6^*7)^*-8^*-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*8^*-7+6+5)^*(4^3/2-1)$
9303	15987	$1+2+3-(45^*-6^*7+89^*-AB)$	$-BA+9-(8+7^*-6^*54^*-3^*2^*-1)$
9304	15988	$-1-2^*(-3-4^*5^*6)^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8-(7+6)-(-5^*4)^3)^*2^1$
9305	15989	$-1+23+4^*56^*-7^*-8-9^*-AB$	$-B+A+987+6^*54^*32-1$
9306	15990	$1-2^*(-3-4^*5^*6)^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6+5^5(4^3/2)-1$
9307	15991	$1+23-4^*56^*7^*-8-9^*-AB$	$B+A+9+8^*7^*6+5^5(4+3-2+1)$
9308	15992	$(-1+2+(-3^*-4-5^*6^*7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8^*7^*-65^*-4+321$
9309	15993	$1-((-2^*(-3+4^5)+6^*7)^*8+9)-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8-(7+6+(-5^*4)^3))/2^1-1$
930A	15994	$1-2+34^*56-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9+(-8-7+6-(-5^*4)^3)^*2^*1$
930B	15995	$-1-2^*(3+4+5+6^*(78-9AB))$	$-B-(A9-8-7^*-6^*54^*3^*-2+1)$
9310	15996	$-12-(34-567-89AB)$	$-B-A9+8+7^*-6^*54^*3^*-2^*1$
9311	15997	$1^2-((3-4)^5-6^*(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A+9876-543-21$
9312	15998	$1+2-34^*-56+789A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*5^*4^*-32+1$
9313	15999	$-1+2-34-56^*(-7-89-AB)$	$B-A+9876-543-21$
9314	16000	$1^*-2^*34^*(5-6-78-9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-9876+543)-2^*1$
9315	16001	$-12+34^*-5^*-67+89-A^*-B$	$-B-(A-9876)-(543+2-1)$
9316	16002	$12^*(34-5-(6-789)-A+B)$	$-BA+9+(-8+7-6)^*-5^*(4+321)$
9317	16003	$-12-34^*-56+789A+B$	$-B-(A-9876+543)-(-2+1)$
9318	16004	$1-(-23+4)+567^*(8-9+A+B)$	$-B-A+9876-543-2^*-1$
9319	16005	$-1^*(2^3+4-5^*-6^*7)^*-8^*9+A+B$	$-B-(A-9876)-(-543-2-1)$
931A	16006	$-12+34+567^*(8-9+A+B)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7^*-6+5+4^3)^*2+1$
931B	16007	$-1-2-(34-567)+89AB$	$BA9-(-8765+432+1)$
9320	16008	$1^*-2-(34-567)+89AB$	$BA9+8765-432^*1$
9321	16009	$1+23+45^*6^*7-89^*-AB$	$BA9+8765-432+1$
9322	16010	$(-1+(-2-3)^*(-4^*5-6^*7^*8))^*9+A-B$	$-B+A^*9^*8+7^*6^*5^*(-4+32)+1$
9323	16011	$-1-(-2-(-34+567)-89AB)$	$-B-A-9^*-8-7^*-6^*-5^*(-43-21)$
9324	16012	$1^*2-34+567+89AB$	$-B+A-98-7^*6^*54^*3^*-2+1$
9325	16013	$1+2-34-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A+987+6^*54^*32+1$
9326	16014	$1^*-2^*(-3+4^*5)^*(678-9AB)$	$B+A-9+(8^*-7+6)^*-5^*4^3+2^*1$
9327	16015	$1+234+(5+6)^*(7-(8-9AB))$	$-B-A+9+8+7+(-6+(-5^*4)^3)^*-2/1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9328	16016	$12 * (-3 - (45+6) - 78+9A*B)$	$B*(A98+7-(6-(-54-(32-1))))$
9329	16017	$-1-2*(345-678*9-A*-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8-7+6-(-5*4)^3)*2/1$
932A	16018	$-1-23-4-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A+9*8+(7+6)*(-5*(4+3))^2\wedge1$
932B	16019	$-1*(23-(-4-(-567-89AB)))$	$-B+A+9876-543-2-1$
9330	16020	$1234-5+6-7+89A*B$	$-B-(-A-9876+543-2*-1)$
9331	16021	$1234-5*-6*7-89*-AB$	$-B+A-(-9876+543-(-2+1))$
9332	16022	$1234-5-6+7+89A*B$	$-B+A+9876-543*(2-1)$
9333	16023	$-1-2*3-(4+56)*(7-89-AB)$	$-B+A-(-9876-(-543+2-1))$
9334	16024	$12-34+567+89AB$	$BA9+87+6*54*(32-1)$
9335	16025	$-1-2*-3*-4+567+89AB$	$-B-(-A-9876+543-2-1)$
9336	16026	$-1-23-(-4-567)+89AB$	$B-A+9876-(543-2)*1$
9337	16027	$-12-3-456*-7-89*-A*B$	$-B-A+9876-543+21$
9338	16028	$1-23+4-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A+9+(-8-7*6)*-5*4^3-2\wedge1$
9339	16029	$-12-3-4+567+89AB$	$B+A+9+(8+7+6-5+4)^3*2-1$
933A	16030	$-12*(34-5+67-89A+B)$	$B+A987+(-6-54)*-32*-1$
933B	16031	$1-23+4*5+67*(-8*-9+AB)$	$B+A+9+(8+7+6-5+4)^3*2+1$
9340	16032	$1234+5-6+7+89A*B$	$-B+A+9876-(-5*4*-32+1)$
9341	16033	$1*2+3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9-A*B$	$-B+A+9876+5*-4*32*1$
9342	16034	$1234-(-5-6-7+89A*-B)$	$-BA+9876-(-5+432-1)$
9343	16035	$-12+3-(-4-567-89AB)$	$B-A+9876+5*4*-32*1$
9344	16036	$(-1+2*(-3+4*5)*6)*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B-A+9876-5*4*32+1$
9345	16037	$-12-3+4-(-567-89AB)$	$-B-A+9+8*7*6+5+4321$
9346	16038	$1*2*(3-4)*((-56-7)*(-8+9A)+B)$	$-B*(-A-9-8)*(76-(54-3)+21)$
9347	16039	$(1+2+3)^4/-5*(-6-7/8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(9+(8+7+6-5+4)^3)*2\wedge1$
9348	16040	$-1*(2-3*-4-(-567+89AB))$	$B+A+9+(-8+7+6-(-5*4)^3)*2\wedge1$
9349	16041	$1+2-3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A+9876-543-2-1$
934A	16042	$1-2-(3+4-567)+89AB$	$-BA+9876-(-5+432)-1$
934B	16043	$-12+3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A-(-9876+543+2-1)$
9350	16044	$1234+5+6+7+89A*B$	$-BA+9876+5-432+1$
9351	16045	$-1*2-3+4+5+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-543+2-1$
9352	16046	$1*(2-3)*(-4-567-89AB)$	$B+A+9876-543-2*-1$
9353	16047	$1*-2+3-4+567+89AB$	$-B+A+9876-543+21$
9354	16048	$1-2-(-3+4)+567+89AB$	$B+A+9+(-8-7+6+(-5*4)^3)*-2*1$
9355	16049	$1-2*3+4+567+89AB$	$B-A+9876-543+21$
9356	16050	$1-2-3-(-4-567)+89AB$	$B+A+9+8+7+6+(-5*-4)^3*2-1$
9357	16051	$1*2+3-4-(-567-89AB)$	$-BA-(-9-8765)-43*-21$
9358	16052	$-1+2-3-(-4-567-89AB)$	$B+A9*-8+7*(6-(-54*32-1))$
9359	16053	$1+2-(-3+4)*-567+89AB$	$B+A-9*-8*7+(-6\wedge5+4*3)*-2/1$
935A	16054	$-1-2-(-3-4-567-89AB)$	$B+A-9*-8*7-(-6\wedge5+4*3)*2+1$
935B	16055	$12-3-456*-7-89A*-B$	$B+A+9876+5*4*-32*-1$
9360	16056	$1-(2-(3-(-4-567-89AB)))$	$B+A+9876+5*4*-32+1$
9361	16057	$123-(-456+7-89AB)$	$B+A+9+8+7+(-6+(-5*4)^3)*-2/1$
9362	16058	$-1+2+3+4+567+89AB$	$-BA+9*8-7*6*5*4*-3*-2*1$
9363	16059	$-1-(2*3*4-567-89AB)$	$B+A+(9\wedge(8-7)-6)\wedge5*(4\wedge3+2)\wedge1$
9364	16060	$-1*(-23+45-6)*(78-(9+A))*-B$	$B*(A-9+876-54*-3+21)$
9365	16061	$1-(2-3*4)-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A-(9-8*7+6-(-5*-4)^3*2+1)$
9366	16062	$-1-(23-45+67*(8*-9-AB))$	$B+A-9*-8*7-((-6\wedge5+4+3)*2+1)$
9367	16063	$12+3-4-(-567-89AB)$	$B+A-9*-8*7+(-6\wedge5+4+3)*-2*1$
9368	16064	$12-3*-4*567+89AB$	$B+A+9-8+7*6+(5*4)^3*2\wedge1$
9369	16065	$12-3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A-9-8*7*6+5+4\wedge(3*2+1)$
936A	16066	$-12+3*4*(56-7+89A+B)$	$B-A+9+876+5+43*21$
936B	16067	$1-2+3+4-6-7*(8+9)*-AB$	$B+A+9*8+(-7-6-(-5*4)^3)*2/1$
9370	16068	$1-2-3+4+5+6+7*8*9+A+B$	$B+A-9*(-8*(7-6\wedge5/-4*3^2-2)+1)$
9371	16069	$1-23*-456-7-89A+B$	$B+A-(-9876+543-21)$
9372	16070	$1\wedge2-3\wedge4+5\wedge6+7*8*9+A+B$	$BA98+7*-6*(5+43*2*1)$
9373	16071	$123-(-456-(7+89AB))$	$-B*(-A-(-9+8)-(-76-543*-2))*1$
9374	16072	$-1+23-4+567+89AB$	$B+A+9+(-8-7-6-(-5*-4)^3)/-2\wedge-1$
9375	16073	$1+2*(-3-4)*(-56-78+9A*-B)$	$B+A+9-8*7*6-5+4\wedge(3*2+1)$
9376	16074	$123*(4+5-6+7+89-A-B)$	$B+A+9+8*7+(-6-(-5*4)^3)*2\wedge1$
9377	16075	$-1+2-3+456-7*89*(-A-B)$	$BA9+8*7*6*5*4-32*1$
9378	16076	$-12+34+567+89AB$	$-B+A+9+8*7-6*(-54+32)*1$
9379	16077	$1+2*-3-4*-56*7*8-9A*-B$	$B+A+9*8*7-6\wedge5*(4-3*2)\wedge1$
937A	16078	$1-((-2*-3)\wedge(4+5-6)+7)*-8*9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7+6\wedge5\wedge(4-3)*2+1$
937B	16079	$1-2-3*(-4\wedge5*-6*-7/8+9)-(A+B)$	$B-(-A-9)-(-8*765-4321)$
9380	16080	$-1+23-(-4-567)+89AB$	$B+A-(9+8*7*6*(54-32)*-1)$
9381	16081	$123-456*-7-8*-9AB$	$BA98-(7-6*(-543+21))$
9382	16082	$1+23+4-(-567-89AB)$	$-B*(-A-987-65-(4-3-21))$
9383	16083	$1-2\wedge3-4*-5*-6*(-7-8)*9-A*B$	$B+A+9-8*7*6+5+4\wedge(3*2+1)$
9384	16084	$-1*2*3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9-(A+B)$	$-B-A-9-(87-(-6+5))*4*(-32-1)$
9385	16085	$-1+(-2+3+4*-5*6)*(-7-8)*9+A+B$	$-BA+9*87+654*3+21$
9386	16086	$1+2*3-4*5*-6*7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8*7*6*(-5*-4)^3/(2+1)$
9387	16087	$-1-2+3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A-9*(-8-7)*(-6*-5*4-(3-2))+1$
9388	16088	$1*-2+3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+(-6-(-5*4)^3)*2*1$
9389	16089	$1-23*(4+5+6*-78)+9AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+(-6-(-5*4)^3)*2+1$
938A	16090	$(-1-2*(3-4\wedge5+6+7))*8-9-(A+B)$	$BA-9*-8-7*(65+4)*(-3-21)$
938B	16091	$1-23*-456-789-AB$	$B+A-9*-8*7+(-6\wedge5-4-3)*-2\wedge1$
9390	16092	$1*2+3+4+567+89AB$	$-B-A-(-98-7)*(65+43+2+1)$
9391	16093	$1+2+3+4+567+89AB$	$-B*(-A-9-876-54-3-21)$
9392	16094	$12345-678*9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8+7-(6-(-5*4)^3*2)\wedge1$
9393	16095	$-1-2*(-3+4+5+678)*(-9-A+B)$	$B-A-(-98+76)*(5+432*1)$
9394	16096	$-1*2\wedge3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8-(-7+6+(-5*4)^3)*2+1$
9395	16097	$1-2\wedge3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A-(9+8-7*(-6+5*(4+32)))$
9396	16098	$-1*2-3*(-4\wedge5*-6*-7/8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+98*(-76+5*43-21)$
9397	16099	$1-2-3*(-4\wedge5*-6*-7/8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+9-8+7*6*(-5-4)*(3-21)$
9398	16100	$1234-(-5-67)+89A*B$	$B+A+9+8+7-6*(-5*4)^3/(2+1)$
9399	16101	$1\wedge2-3*(-4\wedge5*-6*-7/8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+98+7*6*5*4*3*2-1$
939A	16102	$1*2-3*(-4\wedge5*-6*-7/8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+98-7*6*5*4*3*2*-1$
939B	16103	$-1-2*3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8+7*6-(-5*4)^3)*2\wedge1$
93A0	16104	$12+3+4+567+89AB$	$B+A-9+8+(-7*6-(-5*4)^3)*2\wedge1$
93A1	16105	$1-2*3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-(-87+65)*432+1$
93A2	16106	$-1*2*3*4+5\wedge6+7*8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8+7+6+(-5*-4)^3*2\wedge1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
93A3	16107	$-1*(23+456-(7-89))*(-A-B)$	$BA9+8*76*5*4+3*2*-1$
93A4	16108	$12+3+4*5*-6*-7+89AB$	$-B+A9-(87-65)*(-432-1)$
93A5	16109	$1234+56+7+89A*B$	$B+A-9*-8*(-7*(-6*5-(-4/3)^2)+1)$
93A6	16110	$1234+5+67-89A*-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*-7+6)*5+4^A(3*2+1)$
93A7	16111	$1+(-2-3)*4+5^A6-7*-8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8+7-((-6+(-5*4)^3)*2+1)$
93A8	16112	$(-1-2*(3-4^A5+6+7))*8-9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9+(8*-7+6)*(-5*4^A3-2^A1)$
93A9	16113	$-1-2-3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9+8*-76*5*-4-(3-2-1)$
93AA	16114	$-1*2-3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*8*7+6+5^A(4*3/2^A1)$
93AB	16115	$-1-2-3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B*(-A98+7+65+4+3)*(2-1)$
93B0	16116	$-1+2+34*(56-7)-89*-AB$	$B+A+((-9+8-7)*-6-(-5*4)^3)*2-1$
93B1	16117	$-12-34*-5*(67-8+9)+AB$	$B+A+(-9*8+(7+6-5)^A4)*(3+2-1)$
93B2	16118	$1*2-3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6*5)+4^A(3*2+1)$
93B3	16119	$1*-23*(-4+56*(-7+8))*-9-A+B$	$B+A+9*8+(-7-6+(-5*4)^A3)*-2/1$
93B4	16120	$1*2*(3-4+56+7*8*9+A+B)$	$BA+9*876-54*3*21$
93B5	16121	$12345+6*(-7-(-8+9AB))$	$BA9+8+76*5*(4-(-3-21))$
93B6	16122	$1^A2-3-4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*7-6*(-5*4+3)^A2+1)$
93B7	16123	$1*2-3-4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*8-7*6*5+4^A(3*2+1)$
93B8	16124	$-1-2-3*-4*(56+7)+89AB$	$-B-A+9*8*7*6*5+4^A(3+2)+1$
93B9	16125	$1-2^A3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8+(7+6*5*4)^A(3-2+1)$
93BA	16126	$-1*-2*(-3-(456-7+89-A))*-B$	$B*(A98-76)+5-4-3+2*1$
93BB	16127	$-1+23*456-(-78+9A*B)$	$-B-(-A987-65*(4-3+2+1))$
9400	16128	$12*(3+4+5+6+7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A*-9-8*-765+4321$
9401	16129	$1-23*-456+78+9A*-B$	$B-A+9*8*7*(6+5+4+3+2*-1)$
9402	16130	$1+2+3-4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8*-7+6)*(-5*4^A3-2^A1)$
9403	16131	$1+2*3+4+56+7+89AB$	$-BA+9876-54-321$
9404	16132	$1-2+3456+(-7-8*-9A)*B$	$B+A-9-(8+7*6*5*4*-3*-2*-1)$
9405	16133	$1+2^A3-4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA+987-6*-54*-32*-1$
9406	16134	$1-2+3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA-(-987-6*-54*-32)+1$
9407	16135	$1-2+3*4^A5*6*7/8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+7*6+(5*4)^A3*2^A1$
9408	16136	$1^A2+3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B-A9*(-8-7-6+5+4-3+2+1)$
9409	16137	$1*2+3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B*(-A98-7-6+5+4+3+2)*1$
940A	16138	$1+2+3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*-6*(-5-4*3)*2+1$
940B	16139	$1+2+3*4^A5*6*7/8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9/8-7)*(6-5*4)^A3-(2+1)$
9410	16140	$-1*(-23-4+5+6)*(-78*-9-A-B)$	$BA-(-9876+543)-21$
9411	16141	$-1-2*-345-67+89AB$	$BA9+8*76*5*4*(-3-2-1)$
9412	16142	$-12*(-34-5+6-789+A-B)$	$-BA+9876+5*43*2*-1$
9413	16143	$1-2*-345-67+89AB$	$-BA+9876+5*43*2+1$
9414	16144	$1-2-345*6+(-78-9)*-AB$	$-B+A98+7+6*5*4*3*2*1$
9415	16145	$1+23+4-(-5+6+7+89)*-AB$	$B+A+9*8*7-6+5^A(4*3/2)+1$
9416	16146	$1*23*(4-(56*7+8-9)+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7*6)*-5*(-4^A3*2-1)$
9417	16147	$(-1-2*3^A4)*(5+(-6-7)*8)+9-(A-B)$	$B-A9*8-765*(-4*3-2+1)$
9418	16148	$1*(2+3)*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B*(A98-7-65-4+3-2-1)$
9419	16149	$-123-4*-5*(678-9-AB)$	$BA98+765*-4-3*21$
941A	16150	$(-1+2-3^A4)*(-5*6*7+8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6*5*4-3)^A2/1$
941B	16151	$-1+2*3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9-8*-76*-5*-4-32*-1$
9420	16152	$123-45*6*-7-89*-AB$	$B+A98-7+6*5*4*-32*-1$
9421	16153	$-1-2-3*-4*5*6*7-8*-9AB$	$-B-A-(-9876+5+432+1)$
9422	16154	$-12-345-(6+7)*(-89A-B)$	$-B-A+9876-5+432*-1$
9423	16155	$1-2+3*4*-5*-6*7+8*9AB$	$-B-A+9876-5-(432-1)$
9424	16156	$-12*(3-4-56+78+9*-AB)$	$B+A+9*8*7+6+5^A(4*3/2^A1)$
9425	16157	$1-2+3*4^A5*6*7/8+9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7+6+5^A(4*3/2)+1$
9426	16158	$(-1+2^A3)*4+5^A6-7*-8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9+(8-7*(6-(5*4+3)))^A2-1$
9427	16159	$1+23*4+56+7+89AB$	$B*(-A-(9-87-654)+321)$
9428	16160	$1*2^A3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+98+7*(6-543)*(-2-1)$
9429	16161	$1+2^A3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9-(-8765+4+321)$
942A	16162	$1*2^A3+4+5^A6+7*8*9+A+B$	$BA+9876-543-2-1$
942B	16163	$-1/-2*(-3*-4^A5/-6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	$-B-(A-9876-(5-432)+1)$
9430	16164	$(-1-2)*-3*4+5^A6-7*-8*9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-(-543-2))+1$
9431	16165	$1+2+3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A+B$	$-B-(A-9876)+5-432+1$
9432	16166	$12+3*4*(5-(-6+78)+9AB)$	$BA-(-9876+543)-(-2+1)$
9433	16167	$(-1-2*3^A4)*(-5+(-6-7)*8)+9+A+B$	$BA-(-9876-(-543-2*-1))$
9434	16168	$-1+2+34*5-(-6-7)*(89A-B)$	$BA+9876-543+2+1$
9435	16169	$-1+(2+3)^A4+5^A6-7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9+8765+4-321$
9436	16170	$12*(34-(5-6-789)-(A-B))$	$-B*(-A-(9+876)+543)*(2+1)$
9437	16171	$1+(2+3)^A4+5^A6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8+7/6)*(5-(4^A(3+2)+1))$
9438	16172	$((1^A2+3)^A4+5)*(6+7*8)-9+A-B$	$-B-A-(-9-8765+43*21)$
9439	16173	$1234+5+6*(-7-89)*(-A-B)$	$-B+A+9876-(5+432+1)$
943A	16174	$1*2*3*4+5^A6+7*8*9+A+B$	$-B-(-A+9-(8765+43*21))$
943B	16175	$(-1+(-2*-3)^A4*5/6)*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876-5*-4+321)$
9440	16176	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^A5*-6*-7/8-9)+A+B$	$B-A+9876-(5+432)*1$
9441	16177	$1-(2+3*4^A5-6^A7)/(8+9)-A*B$	$BA+9876+5*-4*32+1$
9442	16178	$-1-2*-345-(-6*-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9-8-7*6*5+4^A(3*2+1)$
9443	16179	$1-2*(3+(-4^A5+6+7)*8)+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*8*(7+6-5+4+3)^A2/1$
9444	16180	$1^A2^A3-4*-5*-6*(-7-8)*9-(A+B)$	$B+A+9+(8*-7+6)*(-5*4^A3-(2+1))$
9445	16181	$(-1-(2^A3+4*5))*(-6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B-A+9+87*(-6*-5*4-(-32+1))$
9446	16182	$1+(-2-3*(4+5))*(-6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA-9-8*-765+4321$
9447	16183	$12345-678*9+A*B$	$-B+A+9876+5-432-1$
9448	16184	$(1-2*3)^A4+5^A6+7-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876+5-432*1$
9449	16185	$1-23-4*-56*-7*-8+9AB$	$-B+A+9876-(-5+432)+1$
944A	16186	$-1-2*(3+(-4^A5-(-6-7)*8)-9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A9-87*-6*(-54+32)*1)$
944B	16187	$1+(2+3)^A4+5^A6+7-8*9-(A-B)$	$B-(A-9876)-(-5-(-432+1))$
9450	16188	$123-4*5-67*(-8*9-AB)$	$BA*(98+76-54-(3+2+1))$
9451	16189	$-12+3456-7+8*9A*B$	$B+A9-8*-765+4321$
9452	16190	$1234+56*(78-9+AB)$	$BA-(-9876-(-543+2+1))$
9453	16191	$(-1+2+3)*(-4^A5-6*-7*8*9)+A-B$	$-BA98-76-5*-4321$
9454	16192	$1+2-3*4*(5+(-6-7)*89)-AB$	$B*(A98-7-65-4-(-3-(2-1)))$
9455	16193	$1*-2*3-4*-5*-6*(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*((-8-7)*-6*-5*4+3)-(-2-1)$
9456	16194	$1-2*3-4*-5*-6*(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5-(-4+321)$
9457	16195	$1+(-2+3^A4)*-5*(6-7*8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876+5-(-432-1))$
9458	16196	$1-2*(-345-(-6-7))+89AB$	$-BA-(-9876-5-(-4-321))$
9459	16197	$(-1+(-2*-3)^A4*5/6)*(7+8)-9+A+B$	$B-(-A-9876)-5-432+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
945A	16198	-12-3*-45*6-(-7-89AB)	BA-9*8+7*6*-54*-3*2*1
945B	16199	-1+23*456-789-(A+B)	B+A-9*8+(-7-6)*5^4/(-3/2+1)
9460	16200	-1*23*(-45-67*-8+9*-AB)	BA+9-8*-765+4321
9461	16201	-1-(-2+3*(4+5*(6-789)+AB))	BA9-87-6*54*-32-1
9462	16202	1-(-2-3+45*-6*7+89A*-B)	BA98+765*-4-(-3+21)
9463	16203	-12+3456+7+8*9A*B	B+A-9*(-8*7-6)*(5*4+3^2)^1
9464	16204	12345-678*9+AB	-BA+9876+5+4-321
9465	16205	12345-6*(-7-(8-9AB))	B+A+9876+5-432-1
9466	16206	1234-5*-6+7+89*AB	B+A+9876+5+432*-1
9467	16207	-1*2+3^4+5^6+7*8*9+A-B	B+A+9876-(-5+432-1)
9468	16208	1-2+3^4+5^6+7*8*9+A-B	BA9-87-6*(54*-32-1)
9469	16209	(-1+2)*3^4+5^6-7*-8*9+A-B	B+A+9+((-8-7)*-6-(-5*4)^3)*2-1
946A	16210	1^2+3^4+5^6+7*8*9+A-B	B+A+9+((-8-7)*-6-(-5*4)^3)*2/1
946B	16211	1-(-2+3-4*-56*-7*8-9AB)	-BA+9+8*(76-543)*(-2-1)
9470	16212	-1*-2*(3+4)*(56+789-(A+B))	-BA-98-76*(-54+3)*(-2+1)
9471	16213	-1+2-3*45*-6+7+89AB	B-A987+65*(-4+321)
9472	16214	-1-(2-3456-7)+8*9A*B	B+A+9+8765-43*-21
9473	16215	123-456*-7+89*-A*-B	-BA-(-9876+5*-4)-321
9474	16216	1-(2-3456)+7+8*-9A*-B	B+A-9*(-8-7)*-6*-5*4-3*2+1
9475	16217	123-4+567+89AB	-B+A+9876+54*3*(-2-1)
9476	16218	1*-2*-3*-45*(6*7+8-9*A-B)	BA98+765*-4-3*-2*-1
9477	16219	-1-23*-456-789-(-A+B)	B+A-9*(-8-7)*-6*-5*4-(3-2)-1
9478	16220	1-(-2-3456-(7+8*-9A*-B))	BA+9+87*6*(54-32)+1
9479	16221	1-2*-345+6-(7-89AB)	B+A+9*8*(7+6-5+4+3)^2/1
947A	16222	1-23*-456+789*(A-B)	BA98-765*4-(3-2)-1
947B	16223	-1+2*-34*(-56-7)+8*9A*B	B-A*-9*(87+65)+4*-3*(-2+1)
9480	16224	1*(-23+45)*-6*(-78+9-A-B)	BA98+765*-4*(3-2)*1
9481	16225	123+4+567+89AB	-B*(A-987-(-6+54+3)-21)
9482	16226	-12*(-345-6*78+9-AB)	BA-(98-76*-5*4*-3*(2+1))
9483	16227	1^2-(-3-4*-5*-6*(7+8))*9+A-B	B+A-9*(-8-7)*-6*-5*4+3+2+1
9484	16228	12-(-3+4*-56*7*8)+9AB	B+A-9*(-8-7)*-6*-5*4+3*2+1
9485	16229	1+2-(-3-4*-5*-6*(7+8))*9+A-B	-B+A987-(6+54*3+2+1)
9486	16230	-1*-2-(-3-4*-5*-6*(7+8))*9-(A-B)	BA98-765*4+3+2+1
9487	16231	12+3456+7-8*-9A*B	BA98-765*4-(-3*2-1)
9488	16232	(-1-2*(3-4^5)-(-6+7))*8+9+A-B	B+A+(-9-8-((-7-6)/5^4-4+3))*2+1
9489	16233	1-2*(-3-(4^5-(6+7)))*8+9+A-B	-BA+987+6*54*(32+1)
948A	16234	1+2+3^4+5^6+7*8*9+A+B	-B-A-9*(-8*7/6+5)+4*(3^2+1)
948B	16235	1-2*-345-(-6-7-89AB)	B+A-9*(-8-7)*(-6*-5*4+3^2)-1
9490	16236	1234-5*6*-7+89A*B	-B*(A-(98+76+5-43*-21))
9491	16237	-1+23+4*-56*-7*8+9AB	B+A+(9+8+(-7-6)*5^4)/(-3/2+1)
9492	16238	-1+(2+3)^4+5^6+7-8-9+A-B	BA98-7*6*(54+32+1)
9493	16239	-1-2*-34*5+6*(7+8+9)*-A*-B	-BA98-7*6-5*-4321
9494	16240	12*(34-(-56-789-A)+B)	B+A-9*(-8*(-7-6*-5*4)+3)*2+1
9495	16241	-1+23*456-789-(-A-B)	-B*-A+(-9-8)*-7-(-6+(-5*4)^3)*2/1
9496	16242	1+(2+3)^4+5^6-7+8-9+A-B	-B+A987+6-54*-32*-1
9497	16243	1-2+(34-(56-7)-89)*-AB	-B+A987+6+54*-32+1
9498	16244	-1*(23-4+5+6+7+8+9)*-AB	-B+A+98+7*6*-54*-3*2+1
9499	16245	123*(4-5)*(-67-8-9+A+B)	B+A-9*-8*((-7*-6+5^4)/3+2+1)
949A	16246	-12+3*-4*(5-67-89A-B)	B-A+9*-8-7*(-6-543)*(-2+1)
949B	16247	1-2+(3+4)^5+(-6-7*8)*9+A-B	-B*(-A98-7-6+54+3+21)
94A0	16248	123+456-7*89*(A-B)	B+A+9+(8*7*6-5)*(4+3)^2-1
94A1	16249	1+(2+3)^4+5^6+(7-8)^9+A-B	BA9-8*7+6*-54*-32*1
94A2	16250	1+(2+3)^4-5^6/(7-8)^9+A-B	B+A+(-9*-8-(-7*6+(-5*4)^3))*2+1
94A3	16251	-12-345*-6+789A-B	B+A987-6+54*-32-1
94A4	16252	1-2*3-(-4/(-5+6))^7-8-9-A*B	-B-A+9876-54-321
94A5	16253	(-1+(-2-3)/4-5*6)*-7*8*9+A-B	-B-A+(-9*-8+7)*(6-5*-4*(3^2+1))
94A6	16254	1*23*(-456-(-789-AB))	B+A-9-8-(-7-6)*5^4/(3/2-1)
94A7	16255	(1-2*3)^4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B	B+A+9876-5*4*(3+21)
94A8	16256	1+2345-6+(-7-89)*A*-B	B+A+(-9-8)*7-6*5+4^3(3*2+1)
94A9	16257	(1-2*3)^4+5^6+7-8+9+A-B	B-A98-76*54*-3-2*1
94AA	16258	1*2*(-34+5678-9AB)	-B*(-A-987-65+4+3+2-1)
94AB	16259	1-2*(34-5678+9AB)	-BA+9876+54-321
94B0	16260	1+(2+3)^4+5^6-7+8+9+A-B	-B-A-9*(-8*-7*-6*5-4^3*2-1)
94B1	16261	123+45-67*(8*-9-AB)	B-A+(-9+8*7)*6+(-5*-4)^3*2^1
94B2	16262	-1-(2-345*6)+789A-B	BA98-765*4-32*-1
94B3	16263	-1*(-2*3-4^5*(6-(-7/8-9)))-(-A-B)	B+A*-9*(-87-65)-(-43-2)-1
94B4	16264	(1^2+3)^4(-4+5+6)-7*(8+9)+A-B	B+A987+6+54*-32*1
94B5	16265	(1-2*3)^4+5^6-7-8+9+A+B	B-A9*(87-65-4*32*1)
94B6	16266	(1+(2+3)^4)*(5+6+7+8)-9+A-B	B+A+9*((-8-7)*-6*5*4+3+2)^1
94B7	16267	1-(-2-3-4*-5*-6*(7+8))*9+A+B	-BA+9876+54*-3*2-1
94B8	16268	1+2+345*6+789A-B	-BA98-7-6-5*-4321
94B9	16269	-1+23*45+(67+89A)*B	-B-A*(98+7-(-65-4*-321))
94BA	16270	-1-(-2^(3+4)-5*-6*-7*8)*9+A-B	B+A+(-9-8*7)*(-6+5-4)^3*2-1
94BB	16271	1-(-2*(3-4^5+6)-7)*-8-9+A-B	B+A-9*(8+7)+6-5+4^3(3^2+1)
9500	16272	-1*2*-3*4*(567+8-9A-B)	-B+A+9876-54-321
9501	16273	-12+345*6-(-789A-B)	B+A+(-9+8+(-7-6)*5^4)/(-3/2+1)
9502	16274	-1*2*(3456+7-89A*B)	B-A+9876-54-321
9503	16275	1+2-(3+4+5)*(67-8-9AB)	B+A+9*((-8-7)*-6*5*4+3*2)^1
9504	16276	-12+3*4*-5*-6+7+89*-A*-B	B+A98-7*-6*-54*-3*2*1
9505	16277	-1*-2*(3+(-4*-5*-6+7)*-8*9)+A-B	B-(-A9-8+7*-6*54*-3*2)+1
9506	16278	(-1-2*(3-4^5+6)+7)*8-9+A-B	B+A+(-9*(-8-7)-6-(-5*4)^3)*2-1
9507	16279	12-345*-6-(-789A+B)	BA+9-8*(7+65)*4*-3*-2*-1
9508	16280	-1-2*(3+(-4^5+6)*(-7-(8-9)))+A-B	-B*-A*(98+7-6-(-5-43+21))
9509	16281	1*-23*(4-5-(-67*-8-9-A-B))	B+A+(-9+8)*(7-(6+5)^4)*(3^2+1)
950A	16282	-12*(-34-(5-(-6-(789+A))-B))	-BA98+7-6-5*-4321
950B	16283	1234+56*7+89*AB	-B-A-9*8-7-6+5+4^3(3*2+1)
9510	16284	-1-2+345*6-(-789A-B)	-B+A+9876+5*-43*2+1
9511	16285	(-1*2-3*4^5+6^7)/(8+9)+A-B	B-A+9876+5*-43*2*1
9512	16286	1-2+345*6-(-789A-B)	BA+9+8+7*-6*-54*-3*-2-1
9513	16287	-1-23*-456-(7+89*A)+B	-BA9+8*76*-5*(4+3-2)*-1
9514	16288	-1-(-2+345*-6-(789A+B))	B+A9-(-8-7-6)*543-2-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9515	16289	$1+2345-6-(-789-A)*B$	$B+A+9-(-8+(-7-6)*5^4+3)*2-1$
9516	16290	$1+2+345*6+789A+B$	$-B+A*987-(-6-5*(4+321))$
9517	16291	$12+3-4*5-(-6-78)*-9*(-A-B)$	$-B*(A-987-6-54+3-21)$
9518	16292	$1*2*3^4+5^6+7*8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9*(-8-7-6*5-4^3+2)-1$
9519	16293	$1+2-3*-4*5*6+7+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+9*(8*7*6*5+4^3+2)^{\wedge}1$
951A	16294	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-54-321$
951B	16295	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*(6-5*-4*(3^2+1))$
9520	16296	$-12*(3-4+5+6-789+A-B)$	$-B-(A-9876)+5*-4-321$
9521	16297	$-1+23*456+7*(-8-9-AB)$	$B+A-9-8*(7+6)+5+4^{\wedge}4(3^2+1)$
9522	16298	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8*(-7-6*-5+4)+3)*2-1$
9523	16299	$-1+2345+6-(-789-A)*B$	$BA98-765*4-3*-21$
9524	16300	$1+(-2-3)*-4*(5-6*(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7)-6*-5+4^{\wedge}(-3*-2+1)$
9525	16301	$12-3*(-4-5*(678-(-9A-B)))$	$B+A-9*((-8-7)*6*-5*4-3^2)-1$
9526	16302	$1*-2*(34-(-567+8)+9*-A)*-B$	$-B+A+98765-43*-21$
9527	16303	$-1*2^{\wedge}3-(4/(5-6))^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$BA9-(8-7)+6*54*32-1$
9528	16304	$-1*-2*(-3-4-(5+6*7-89)-AB)$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*6+(-5*-4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$
9529	16305	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6)-(-5-4^{\wedge}4(3^2+1))$
952A	16306	$-12+3*4*(-56-(-7+8-9AB))$	$BA9+8-7-6*54*-32*1$
952B	16307	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-5-4-321$
9530	16308	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+((-9-(8+7))*-6-(-5*4)^{\wedge}3)*2-1$
9531	16309	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+((-9-8-7)*-6-(-5*4)^{\wedge}3)*2^{\wedge}1$
9532	16310	$-12*(34-5+6+78-9A*B)$	$-B+A987-6*(-54+321)$
9533	16311	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*(-8+(-7-6)*(5+4^3))*-2*1$
9534	16312	$-1-23*(-456-7)+(-8+9A)*-B$	$B+A+(-9-8+(-7-6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)*-2+1$
9535	16313	$1*2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9-((-8+(-7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^2+1)$
9536	16314	$1+2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+(-8-7*(6+5))^*-4^3)^*(2+1)$
9537	16315	$-12345+6*7*8*(-9+AB)$	$-B-A+9876-5-(-4+321)$
9538	16316	$1*2+3-(4/(5-6))^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876-5-432-1$
9539	16317	$1+2+3-(4/(5-6))^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$BA-(9-8765)+43*21$
953A	16318	$(1-2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7*8-9+A-B$	$B-A+9876+5*-4-321$
953B	16319	$-1+2*-34*(5-6-7-(8-9)-AB)$	$B+A+9-(8+7)*6-5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9540	16320	$1+2^{\wedge}3-(4/(5-6))^{\wedge}7-8*9+A-B$	$-BA9-876+543*21$
9541	16321	$-1*-2^{\wedge}3*(-4^{\wedge}5/-6+7*8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
9542	16322	$1+(-2-3)*-4*(5-6*(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	$BA98-7*-6*(-54-32+1)$
9543	16323	$-1*-2*((-3+4^{\wedge}5+6-7)*8-9)+A+B$	$-BA98+7*6-5*-4321$
9544	16324	$-1*-2*(-3-(4-5678+9AB))$	$B*(-A+98)*7*6(6-5)*(-4+3-(-2-1))$
9545	16325	$1-2345+(678+9)*(A+B)$	$-BA98+765*(-4+32)-1$
9546	16326	$-1*2/(3-4^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5-(432+1)$
9547	16327	$-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7+8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+(-5+432)*-1$
9548	16328	$-1-(-2+3-4*5*(-6+7*8)+A*B)$	$BA-(-9876-5)-432+1$
9549	16329	$1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B-(A-9876+5+4)-321$
954A	16330	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$BA*(9+8+7+6-(5+4)-(-3-2-1))$
954B	16331	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-54*(3+2)-1$
9550	16332	$1-23*-456-789-A*-B$	$B-(-A9876*(-54+321))$
9551	16333	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*8+(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
9552	16334	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*8-(7-6-5)^{\wedge}(4+3)+2-1$
9553	16335	$1*23*(456+78-9A-B)$	$B*(A+987-65+4*32+1)$
9554	16336	$1*2*(3-4+5678-9AB)$	$-B-A+9876+5*4-321$
9555	16337	$-1-2-3*45-(6+7)*-89A-B$	$B-A-(-9876+5+4321)$
9556	16338	$12*(3-(45+6-789+A*-B))$	$B+A+9876+5*-4-321$
9557	16339	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3+(-4*(5-6))^{\wedge}7-(8+9)+A-B$	$B-A+9876-(-5+4)-321$
9558	16340	$1*-2*(3-4-5678+9AB)$	$B+A-9*8+7/(6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9559	16341	$-123-(4+5)-((6+7)*-89A-B)$	$-B-A*9*(-87-65)-4*32*-1$
955A	16342	$-1*-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5-(6-7))*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A*9*(87+65)+4*32+1$
955B	16343	$-1-2/(3-4^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(6-7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7*(6+5-432)*1$
9560	16344	$12-34*(-56+7)+89A*B$	$B+A-9+(8-7*-6^{\wedge}5)/(4+(-3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
9561	16345	$1-2/(3-4^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(6-7)*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876+5+4-321$
9562	16346	$-1+23+4*5*(678-(9+AB))$	$-B*(A98+7-65)*(4+3*-2+1)$
9563	16347	$1+2-3-4*5-(6+7)*(-89A+B)$	$-B+A9*(-8+7+6+5+43)-21$
9564	16348	$-1-2*-34*5*67-89AB$	$-B-A98*-7+65*(-4+3*21)$
9565	16349	$-1*(-2+3*4)*-5*(-6*-7*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+9876-5-(4+321)$
9566	16350	$1-2*34*5*-67-89AB$	$-B-A-9-8-7+6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9567	16351	$-1-23*-456-789+AB$	$B+A-9-8-7-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9568	16352	$1*2*(3+4+5678-9AB)$	$-B-A-9-8+7-6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9569	16353	$1-23*-456-(789-AB)$	$B+A-9*-8+(-7+(-6-5)^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
956A	16354	$-1*(23+45-6)*(-78-9A-B)$	$-B-(A-9876+5*-4*32+1)$
956B	16355	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-((-8+(-7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^2+1)$
9570	16356	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A-(-9876+5*-4+321)$
9571	16357	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5-4*3*-21)$
9572	16358	$-1*2^{\wedge}3+(4/(-5+6))^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876+5*-4+321)$
9573	16359	$(1-2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9876+5-4-321$
9574	16360	$1-2*(3-4^{\wedge}5*(-6+7)*8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9876-54*-3*(-2-1)$
9575	16361	$1-2*3-(-4/(-5+6))^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$BA9-8*-7-6*54*32*-1$
9576	16362	$-1*-2*(3*4+5678-9AB)$	$B+A+9-(-876-5)*(-4*3+21)$
9577	16363	$-1-2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6*54*3*2-1$
9578	16364	$-1-23*-456+7-8*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A987-6*54*(3-(-2-1))$
9579	16365	$1-2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
957A	16366	$(1+2+3*4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7*6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2^{\wedge}1$
957B	16367	$1+234-56*(-7-(89+AB))$	$B+A-(-9876-(5+4-321))$
9580	16368	$1*2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$-B*(A-9)*(-87-(654+321))$
9581	16369	$1+2-(3+4-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8-9+A-B$	$-BA9-8+76*(-54-3)*(-2-1)$
9582	16370	$1-2-3+4^{\wedge}(5-6)^{\wedge}7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8-7-6-5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9583	16371	$12345+67*-89-AB$	$-BA98+76-5*-4321$
9584	16372	$1^{\wedge}2-3+4^{\wedge}(5-6)^{\wedge}7+8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5*-43-21$
9585	16373	$-1+2^{\wedge}3(3-4+5*6-7-8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8-7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9586	16374	$-1-2*3-45*-6*7*8-9AB$	$-B+A+9876+6*-54*(-32-1)$
9587	16375	$1+2^{\wedge}3(3-4+5*6-7-8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9876+5*4*(3-21)$
9588	16376	$1+23*456+78*-9-AB$	$B+A+(9-8)^{\wedge}7-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
9589	16377	$-1+234+567+89AB$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6*(5-4^3+2-1)$
958A	16378	$1*234+567+89AB$	$B+A-(-9876+5*-4)-321$
958B	16379	$1+234-(-567-89AB)$	$B*(A-9+87-(-654-321))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9590	16380	$-12 * (-34 - 5) * (6 - 7) * (89 - AB)$	$-B - (A - 9876) - (-54 + 321)$
9591	16381	$1 - 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9592	16382	$123 - 4 * -56 * 7 * 8 + 9AB$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9593	16383	$1 + 2 - 3 * -4 * (56 - (7 - 8 - 9A * B))$	$B - (-A987 - 6 + 543 * (2 + 1))$
9594	16384	$(1 + 2 + 3 * 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 - 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9595	16385	$-1 - 2 + 3 * 56 - 7 + 89 * AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9596	16386	$1 * 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 - 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9597	16387	$1 + 2 - 3 - 4 * 5 + (-6 - 7) * (-89A + B)$	$B + A987 - 6 * -54 * -3 * 2 + 1$
9598	16388	$1 * 2 + 3 + 4 \wedge (5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B + A987 - 6 * 5 * (43 + 21)$
9599	16389	$-1 - (-2 - 34 * 56 + 7 - 89 * AB)$	$B + A - 9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \wedge 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
959A	16390	$1 + 2 * 3 + 4 \wedge (5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B * A * (98 - 7 - 6 * -5 - (-4 + 3 * 2 * -1))$
959B	16391	$12 + 3 * 45 * (6 - (7 - 89 - A + B))$	$B - (-A987 - 6 - 5 * (-4 - 321))$
95A0	16392	$12345 + 6 + 78 * 9 * A - B$	$B - A - 98 - 765 * (4 * 3 - (2 + 1))$
95A1	16393	$1 + 2 \wedge (3 - 4 + 5 * 6 - 7 - 8) + 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 / (7 - 6) + 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
95A2	16394	$1 + 2 * 3 + (-5 - 6) * (7 * -8 - 9AB)$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 * -43 - (2 + 1)$
95A3	16395	$1 + 2 + (3 - 4 + 5) \wedge (6 - 7 + 8) + 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 * -43 + 2 * -1$
95A4	16396	$1 + 23 - 4 * 56 * (-78 - (-9 - A) + B)$	$B - A + 9 + 8 - 7 * 6 * (54 - 321)$
95A5	16397	$-1 - 23 * 45 * (-6 - 7) + 89 * (-A - B)$	$-B - (-A987 + 6 + 5 * (-4 + 321))$
95A6	16398	$12 + 3 + 45 * -6 * 7 * -8 - 9AB$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 * 43 + 2 - 1$
95A7	16399	$-12 - 3 * -45 + (-6 + 78) * 9 * (A + B)$	$-BA - (-9876 + 5 * 43 - 2 * 1)$
95A8	16400	$1 * -2 * 34 * (-56 - 7 + 8 - 9 - AB)$	$-B + A + 9876 + 54 - 321$
95A9	16401	$1 + (2 - 3 + 4 - 5 + 6) \wedge 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B * (A98 - 76 + 54 - 32 - 1)$
95AA	16402	$1 * 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B - A - 9876 - (-54 + 321)$
95AB	16403	$1 + 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 - (7 - 6 - 5) \wedge (4 + 3) - 2 - 1$
95B0	16404	$-1 * (-2 + 34 * -56 - (7 - 89 * -AB))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
95B1	16405	$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 - 5 - (-6 - 7) * (89A - B)$	$B + A987 + (6 - 5 + 4) * -321$
95B2	16406	$(1 + 2 * 3 - 4 \wedge 5 + 6 \wedge 7) / (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + (9 + 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4 \wedge 3) \wedge 2 + 1$
95B3	16407	$(1 - 2 + 3) \wedge (4 * 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \wedge 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
95B4	16408	$1 - 23 - 4 - 5 + (67 + 8) * 9 * (A + B)$	$BA9 + 87 + 6 * -54 * 32 * -1$
95B5	16409	$1 + 2 \wedge 3 - (4 / (5 - 6)) \wedge 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA98 - 7 * 6 - (5 + 4) * 321$
95B6	16410	$(1 + 2) \wedge 3 + 4 \wedge (5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 * (765 - 43) * 2 - 1$
95B7	16411	$(1 + 2) \wedge 3 + (-4 / (5 - 6)) \wedge 7 - 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 - 54 * -3 * 2 * -1$
95B8	16412	$1 - 2 * (3 - (-4 + 5 + 6 - 7) * -8 - 9) + A - B$	$-B * (-A - (987 + 65 + 4) - (3 - 2 + 1))$
95B9	16413	$-1 - 23 * -456 + 78 * (-9 + A - B)$	$BA98 + 7 - 65 * (43 + 2 + 1)$
95BA	16414	$1 - (-23 + 4 - (-56 - 78 + 9)) * -A * B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
95BB	16415	$123 - 4 * (-5 + 67 - 89) * AB$	$BA + 9876 - 54 - 321$
9600	16416	$12 + 34 * 56 + 7 + 89 * AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9601	16417	$-1 - 2 * (-34 - 5678 + 9AB)$	$B + A + 9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \wedge (4 + 3) + 2 + 1$
9602	16418	$1 * 2 * (34 + 5678 - 9AB)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9603	16419	$1 - 2 * (-34 - 5678 + 9AB)$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 * (-4 + 321)$
9604	16420	$-12 + 3 * -45 * 6 - 78 * 9 * (-A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5) \wedge (4 + 3) - 2 / 1$
9605	16421	$1234 + 5 * 67 + 89A * B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - (7 - 6) \wedge 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9606	16422	$-12 * (3 + 4 - 56 - 789 + A - B)$	$B + A - 9876 + 54 - 321$
9607	16423	$1 * (-23 + 4 * (-5 - 6 + 7) * (-89 + A)) * B$	$-B * (-A98 + 7 * 6 - 5 + 4 - 3 + 21)$
9608	16424	$12 + 3456 - 7 * -8 * 9 * (A + B)$	$BA98 + 76 * (-5 + 43) * (-2 + 1)$
9609	16425	$1 - 2 * (-3 - (4 \wedge 5 + 6 - 7)) * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA - (-9876 - 5 * -43 * 2 + 1)$
960A	16426	$1 * -2 * (-3 - (4 \wedge 5 + 6 - 7)) * 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$BA + 9876 + 5 * 43 * -2 * 1$
960B	16427	$(1 + 2) \wedge 3 + (-4 * (5 - 6)) \wedge 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B - A * -987 - 6 - 54 * 32 * -1$
9610	16428	$1 * 2 * (-3 + 45 + 67 * 89 - AB)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9611	16429	$-1 + (2 \wedge (-3 + 4) * 5 + 6) + 7) * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9612	16430	$-1 * (-2 - 3) * 45 * (67 - (8 + 9 * (-A + B)))$	$B + A + 9876 - 54 * -3 * -2 - 1$
9613	16431	$((-1 + 2 - 3) * -4 \wedge 5 + 6) * (7 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A - (-9876 + 54 * -3 * -2 * 1)$
9614	16432	$1 \wedge 2 - (-3 - 4 \wedge 5) * (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B - A9 + (-87 - 6 + 543) * 21$
9615	16433	$(-1 + (2 / (3 - 4)) \wedge 5) * (6 - 7 * 8 * 9) + A - B$	$-B - A - 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * (5 - 4 * 3) \wedge 2 - 1$
9616	16434	$(-1 - 2 * (3 \wedge 4 + 5)) * ((-6 - 7) * 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B * (-A98 + 7 - 6 * 54) * 3 * (2 - 1)$
9617	16435	$1 * (-2 * (-3 - 4 \wedge 5) + 6 + 7) * 8 + 9 - A * B$	$-BA - (-9876 - 54 * 3) - 21$
9618	16436	$-1 - 2 \wedge 3 * -4 * (-5 + 6 + 7 * 8) * 9 + A + B$	$B + A + (9 - 8) \wedge 7 + 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9619	16437	$1 + 23 * 456 + 78 + 9 * -A * B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 * (4 + 32 + 1)$
961A	16438	$1 * -2 * (-3 - (4 \wedge 5 - (6 - 7))) * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * -7 * 6 * (5 - 4 * 3) \wedge 2 - 1$
961B	16439	$-1 + 2 / (3 + 4 \wedge 5) \wedge (6 - 7) * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A * 987 + 6 + 54 * -32 * -1$
9620	16440	$-1 * -2 * 3 * 4 * (567 + 8 - (-9 + AB))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9621	16441	$-1 - 2 + 34 * 5 * 6 - 7 + 89AB$	$B + A - 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9622	16442	$-123 + 45 + 6 * 78 * (9 + A + B)$	$B + A + (-9 + 8) * (-7 - 6 * 5) + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9623	16443	$-1 * 23 * (-456 - (-7 + 89) + AB)$	$BA - 98 * 7 * (-6 - 5) + 4321$
9624	16444	$(-1 - 2 * -3 * 4) * (-5 - 6) * (7 - 8 * 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 / (8 - 7) + 6 * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9625	16445	$-1 + 2 + 34 * 5 * 6 - (7 - 89AB)$	$-B * (-A98 - 7 + 6 - (-54 + 3 - 2 + 1))$
9626	16446	$(-1 - 2) * 3 - (4 / (5 - 6)) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-BA98 - 7 + (-65 - 4) * -321$
9627	16447	$1 - (2 - 3 * (4 - 5 * -67)) + 89AB$	$BA9 + 8765 - (4 + 3) * 21$
9628	16448	$1234 * (5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 - A + B)$	$B + A + (9 - 8 + 7) * 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9629	16449	$1 * -2 * 3 + 4 \wedge ((-5 + 6) * 7) + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9 * (8 + 7) * ((6 + 5 \wedge (4 - 3)) \wedge 2 + 1)$
962A	16450	$1 - 2 * 3 - (4 / (5 - 6)) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9 - 8 + 76 * (-54 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
962B	16451	$(-1 - 2 + 3 \wedge 4) * -5 * -6 * 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9630	16452	$-1 - 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 \wedge (6 - 5) + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9631	16453	$-1 * 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9632	16454	$1 - 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + 9876 + 54 * (-3 - 2) + 1$
9633	16455	$(1 + 2 + 3 * 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A9 * -87 + 65 * (4 + 32 - 1)$
9634	16456	$1 * 2 * (-3 - 456 - (-7 - 8 + 9A)) * -B$	$-B * (-A98 - (-7 - (65 + 4 - 3 - 21)))$
9635	16457	$1 * 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + 9 / 8 * (7 + (6 + 5) \wedge 4) \wedge (3 - 2) - 1$
9636	16458	$1 + 2 - (3 + 4 - 5 - 6) \wedge 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$BA + 98 + 76 * 5 * -4 * 3 * (-2 - 1)$
9637	16459	$-1 + 2 - 34 * 5 * -6 + 7 + 89AB$	$BA + 9876 - 5 * 4 - 321$
9638	16460	$1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \wedge 5 - 6 * 7 * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$-BA - 9876 - 54 * 3 * (2 - 1)$
9639	16461	$1 - (-2 + 34 * -5 * 6) - (-7 - 89AB)$	$-BA - (-9876 + 54 * 3) - (-2 + 1)$
963A	16462	$-123 - 4 * 5 + (-6 - 7) * (-89A - B)$	$B + A - 9 + (8 * -7 + 6) * (-5 * (4 \wedge 3 + 2) + 1)$
963B	16463	$1 * 2 + (3 + 4) \wedge 5 - 6 * 7 * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 * -6 * (5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
9640	16464	$-1 * -2 * (3 + 4) * (-56 - 7 * 8 - 9A * B)$	$B + A + 9 * (-876 + 5 * 432 - 1)$
9641	16465	$(1 + 2 + 3 - 4 * 5 + 6 \wedge 7) / (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) * 5 + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9642	16466	$1 - (2 + 3 + 4 + 5 - 6 \wedge 7) / (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + (9 / 8 + 7) * (((-6 - 5 - 4) * 3) \wedge 2 - 1)$
9643	16467	$1 * (-234 - (56 + 789 - A)) * -B$	$B * (A98 + 7 - 6 + 5 * -4 * 3) * (2 - 1)$
9644	16468	$1 + 23 + 4 * 5 * (-6 + 78 * 9) * (-A + B)$	$B + A + 9 / (8 / 7 - 6 + 5) + 4 \wedge (3 * 2 + 1)$
9645	16469	$1 - 23 * -456 + 7 * -89 - AB$	$BA9 + 8765 + 43 * (-2 - 1)$
9646	16470	$-1 * 23 * (456 - (-7 + 89A - B))$	$BA + 9876 - 5 - 4 - 321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9647	16471	$-1+2+3+(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)/(8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8765-4*32+1$
9648	16472	$-123+4*56*7*(8-9+A)+B$	$-BA*(-9-87+6*-5-(-43+21))$
9649	16473	$1+2+3+(-4*5-6^{\wedge}7)/(-8-9)+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876)-(-5-4)*32*-1$
964A	16474	$1+2*3+(-4*5-6^{\wedge}7)/(-8-9)+A-B$	$BA9+8765-4*(32-1)$
964B	16475	$1*2^{\wedge}3+(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)/(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+8*7*6*(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
9650	16476	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7+65*(-43-2)*1$
9651	16477	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*(-4+32+1)$
9652	16478	$-12*(3-(4+5-(6-7+8+9A)))*-B$	$BA+9876-(5-4+321)$
9653	16479	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A-9-((-87+6)*-5*(4-32)+1)$
9654	16480	$-12+3*-45+(6+7)*(89A+B)$	$BA+9876-(-5+4)-321$
9655	16481	$12345-67*89-A-B$	$-BA+9876+5*(4-32)-1$
9656	16482	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5-(4+3)*21$
9657	16483	$-123-4+5-(6+7)*(-89A-B)$	$-BA+9876+5*(4-32)+1$
9658	16484	$-1-23*-456+7-8*(9A-B)$	$-BA+9876-(5+43)*(2+1)$
9659	16485	$-1*-2*(3+(4^{\wedge}5+6)*(-7-(8-9)))+A-B$	$-BA+9876-54*3+21$
965A	16486	$-1+((-2+(-3-4)*5)*-6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8*7^{\wedge}A(-6+5+4)/3*2+1$
965B	16487	$(-1*(-2^{\wedge}3*-4+5)*-6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5*(4-32+1)$
9660	16488	$(-1-2*(3-(4^{\wedge}5+6)+7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-(5-(-4+321)))$
9661	16489	$-12+3-(456-78)*(-9-(A+B))$	$-B*(-A98-(76+5-4*32*1))$
9662	16490	$-1*2*345*(-6-7+8+9-A-B)$	$-BA-9*-8*7*(6-5)*(-4+32-1)$
9663	16491	$(1-(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5-6^{\wedge}7)/(-8-9)-(A-B)$	$B+A+9*(8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}A(4-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
9664	16492	$-1*2*(3+4)*(-56-789-A+B)$	$B+A*(987+6)-54*-32-1$
9665	16493	$-1+2+3+(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)/(8+9)+A+B$	$B+A+9+8*7*6*(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
9666	16494	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3+(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)/(8+9)+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876+5)-(-4*-32+1)$
9667	16495	$(-1-2*3-4^{\wedge}5)*(-6+7-8-9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5+4*-32*1$
9668	16496	$1+23-45+(-6-7)*-89A+B$	$BA+9876+5*-4*(-3+21)$
9669	16497	$1*23*(-4-5+67*8+9-A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8+7)*((-6-5*-4)^{\wedge}3+2)/1$
966A	16498	$1234+56*7-89A*-B$	$-B+A-(-9876-5+4*-3*-21)$
966B	16499	$1-2-345-67*(-89-A*B)$	$BA-(-9876+5*-4)-321$
9670	16500	$-1*(-2-3)*-4*(-567+89-AB)$	$B*-A*(9+8-(-7-6))*-5-4+3+2-1$
9671	16501	$-1-(-2+3*-4*(56+7-8-9A)*-B))$	$B+A+9/8*(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$
9672	16502	$-123-4*-5+(6+7)*(89A+B)$	$B+A+9/8*(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4)+3-2+1$
9673	16503	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+(6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7^{\wedge}A(-6+5+4)*3)*-2*1$
9674	16504	$-1+(-2-3/4-5*6)*-7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5-4*-32+1)$
9675	16505	$-1*(-2-3/4-5*6)*-7*-8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5+4*-32*1$
9676	16506	$-12*(3-(4-56+789)-AB)$	$-BA+9876+5-4*32+1$
9677	16507	$-1*-2*(3+(4^{\wedge}5+6)*(-7-(8-9)))+A+B$	$-B-A+9-(-8*7*(6+(5+4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
9678	16508	$1234-567+89AB$	$-B-(A-9876)+5*(43+2)*-1$
9679	16509	$-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*(-5*-6*7+8-9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5+4*(32-1))$
967A	16510	$-1+2*3*(-45+67)*89+AB$	$BA9-(-8765-4*(-3-21))$
967B	16511	$1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*(-5*-6*7+8-9)+A-B$	$-B*(-A-9)*(-8*-7-6-5-4-32*-1)$
9680	16512	$-1-(2-3)+4*(5-(-6+7))*8*(9A+B)$	$B+A-9+(-8*7*6)*-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)*1$
9681	16513	$1-2*((-3-(4^{\wedge}5+6+7))*8+9)-A*B$	$-BA+9876-54-3*21$
9682	16514	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3*(4+(-5-6)*7*8)-9+A-B$	$BA98+76*5*(4+3+2)*-1$
9683	16515	$1-(-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*8+9)-A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-5*-43)-21$
9684	16516	$1*-2*(34-5678-9A*-B)$	$-BA-9*(-876+5-432)-1$
9685	16517	$-1-2-(34-5)*-67+89*AB$	$B+A98-(-7-6)*(5-43)*-21$
9686	16518	$1+23-4-5+(6+7)*89A-B$	$-BA+9876+(-54-3)*2*1$
9687	16519	$1-2+(34-5*6)*7*(89+AB)$	$B+A+9*8*7-6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2^{\wedge}1$
9688	16520	$12*(3-(4-5)-(6-7))*(89+AB)$	$BA9+8765+43*2*1$
9689	16521	$-1*2+(3/-4+5)*-6^{\wedge}7/(-8*9)+A-B$	$BA9+8765-(43*2-1)$
968A	16522	$1*2*(-34+567+8*(9-A))*B$	$-BA+9876-5*(43-21)$
968B	16523	$-1+2+345-67*(-8*9-AB)$	$-B-(-A-9876)+5*(-43-2-1)$
9690	16524	$-1*-23*(456+78+9-AB)$	$B+A+9*8*7*6+5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
9691	16525	$1+23*(456+78-(9+AB))$	$B+A-9+(-8^{\wedge}7+6-5)/(-4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
9692	16526	$1*(-2*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$-BA-9*(-876+5-432-1)$
9693	16527	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7+(-6-5^{\wedge}A)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
9694	16528	$1+(-2/(-3*4^{\wedge}5)+6)*(-7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A98-7)+6*54*(32+1)$
9695	16529	$12-(34+5)-6*78*(-9-A-B)$	$-B-A*-987-6*(5*4-3)*-21$
9696	16530	$(-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5)*6*7-(8+9)+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-5*(43+2)*-1)$
9697	16531	$-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*(-5*-6*7+8-9)+A+B$	$B-(A-9876-5*(-43-2)-1)$
9698	16532	$(-1+2-3*(4+(-5-6)*7*8))*9+A-B$	$BA-98-7*-6*(-5+4321)$
9699	16533	$-1-(-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9876+5*(-43+2+1)$
969A	16534	$12*(-3+4+56+789-A+B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7/-6-5)/-4^{\wedge}3*-2+1$
969B	16535	$-123+45-(-6-7)*(89A+B)$	$-BA-(9+87*6*(-5-4)*-3*(-2+1))$
969C	16536	$1-23*(-45+6*-7)+89A*B$	$-B+A+9876+5*-43-2*1$
96A1	16537	$1-(-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*8+9)-(A-B)$	$B+A-9*-8*7+(-6+(-5*4)^{\wedge}3)*-2^{\wedge}1$
96A2	16538	$(-1-2*-3*4)*(-5-6*-7*(8+9))-(A-B)$	$B+A-9*-8*7-((-6+(-5*4)^{\wedge}3)*-2-1)$
96A3	16539	$-1*(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*6*7-8*9+A+B$	$-B+A-(-9876-5*-43-2)-1$
96A4	16540	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5-6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
96A5	16541	$-1-2+34+5+(-6-7)*-89A-B$	$BA98+76+(-5-4)*321$
96A6	16542	$-1*2*(3-(4-5)-6+78*9*-A+B)$	$B-A-(-9876-5*-43)-2*-1$
96A7	16543	$-1*-2^{\wedge}3*-4*(-5-6)*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA+9876-(-54+321)$
96A8	16544	$-1*-2*(34-567-(-8-9+A))*-B$	$-BA+9876-(5+43*2+1)$
96A9	16545	$1+(2*(3+4^{\wedge}5)+6+7)*8+9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876-(-5-43*-2*-1))$
96AA	16546	$(-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5)*6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA9+8765-43-21$
96AB	16547	$-1*(-2^{\wedge}3*-4+5/6)*-7*8*9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876-5*(-4-3)*(2+1))$
96B0	16548	$-12*(34-(-56+7+89A+B))$	$B+A-9+8*(-7-6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$
96B1	16549	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7*8-9)+A+B$	$-BA+9876-54-32-1$
96B2	16550	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*((-4-5*6)*7+8))*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-54+32*-1$
96B3	16551	$1*23*(456-7+8-9-(A+B))$	$BA9+8765+4+3*-21$
96B4	16552	$123+45*6*7*8-9AB$	$BA+9876+54*-3*-2*-1$
96B5	16553	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8+9)-A*B$	$-BA-(-9876-5*4*(-3-2))$
96B6	16554	$-1-2*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5-(6-7)*8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9*((8-7*6)*5+(4+3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
96B7	16555	$-1-(-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*8+9)+A+B$	$-BA+9876+5+43*2*1$
96B8	16556	$-1+(-2^{\wedge}3-(-4^{\wedge}5+6*7))*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9876-5*(43+21)$
96B9	16557	$1-(-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*8+9)+A+B$	$-BA-(-9876+5*4-3*-21)$
96BA	16558	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5-6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9876+5*-43+2*-1$
96BB	16559	$((-1*2+3-4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-(-6+5^{\wedge}A)^{\wedge}3)+2^{\wedge}1$
9700	16560	$1*-2*3*4*5*(6-(7-(-8-9A)+B))$	$-BA-(-9876+5+4+3)-21$
9701	16561	$(-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5*6)*7+8-9-(A+B)$	$B+A+9876-(5*43-(2-1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9702	16562	$1 + ((2-3+4)^5 - (6+7)) * 8^9 - (A-B)$	$B + A + 9876 - 5 * 43 + 2 * 1$
9703	16563	$(-1^* - 2 - 3^*(4 + (-5-6)^*7^8))^9 + A + B$	$B - (-A - 9876 - (-5^*43 - (-2-1)))$
9704	16564	$(-1 + (-2+3^4)^5) * 6^7 + 8+9+A-B$	$B + A + (-9+8^*7)^*(-6-5)/(-4^{\wedge} - 3^*2) - 1$
9705	16565	$(-1 + (-2+3^4)^5 * 6^7) * 7 - (8+9) + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 + 5^* - 43 + 21$
9706	16566	$-1 - 2^{\wedge} 3^*(-4^* - 5^*(-6-7)^*8+9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 + 3 - 21$
9707	16567	$(1^{\wedge} 2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4 * -5^*(-6-7) - 8^*9 + A - B$	$BA98 + 7 - 65^*(43 + 2 - 1)$
9708	16568	$1 + 23 - 4^*5^*(-678 + 9A + B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 43 - 2 - 1$
9709	16569	$-1^*(-2^{\wedge} 3^* - 4 + 5/6)^* - 7^*8^*9 + A + B$	$BA9 + 8765 + (43 + 2)^* - 1$
970A	16570	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge} - 3 + 4 + 5^*6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9 - (A - B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 43 - 2 + 1$
970B	16571	$1 + 2 + (3+4)^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + (-7-8)^*9 - A^*B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - 43 - 21$
9710	16572	$-1^*((-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^*6^*7 + 8) - 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 43 + 2 - 1$
9711	16573	$1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 - (8+9) + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - (43 - 2^*1)$
9712	16574	$-12 - 34^*56 - 78^*(-9 - A)^*B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 43 + 2 + 1$
9713	16575	$-123 - 456 - 78^* - 9^*(A + B)$	$-B - A987 - (654^* - 32 - 1)$
9714	16576	$12^*(3 - (4 - 5 + 67 - 89A) - B)$	$-B - (-A - (9876 - 54^*3 - 21))$
9715	16577	$(-1 + (-2 - 3/4 - 5^*6)^*7)^* - 8^*9 + A - B$	$-B^*(-A - 9 - 87 - 654 - 321)$
9716	16578	$-1 - (-2 - 3) + 45 - (-6 - 7)^*89A + B$	$B - (A - 9876 + 54^*3 + 21)$
9717	16579	$-1^*(2 + 3 + (-4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^*7)^*(8 + 9)) - A^*B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 32 - 1$
9718	16580	$12 + 34 + 5 + (6 + 7)^*89A + B$	$BA9 + 8765 - (4 - 32^* - 1)$
9719	16581	$(-1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5 * 6^7 + 8 - 9 + A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 - 43 - 21$
971A	16582	$(-1 + 2 - 3)^*(-4^{\wedge} 5 - (6 + 7)^*8 - 9 + A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 - 3 - 2 - 1$
971B	16583	$-1234 - 5 - 67^*(-89 - AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 - (-3^* - 2 - 1)$
9720	16584	$1 + 2345 + (-6 - 78)^*(-9A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 - 3 - 2 + 1$
9721	16585	$12 - 3^* - 4^*(5 + (-6 - 7)^* - 89) + AB$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4^* - 3 - 21$
9722	16586	$(1 - 2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7)/(8 + 9) + A - B)$	$-BA - 9 + 8765 - 4^* - 321$
9723	16587	$123^*(4 + 56 - 78 + 9A^*B)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 - 3 + 2^*1$
9724	16588	$1^*(-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 + 3 - (2 + 1)$
9725	16589	$1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - (-4 + 32 - 1)$
9726	16590	$12^*(34 + 5 + 6 - (-789 - A - B))$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 - 21$
9727	16591	$12 - (3 + 4^* - 5) - 6^*78^*(-9 - A - B)$	$B + A - 9^*8 + ((-7 - 6)^*5 - 4^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
9728	16592	$-1^*((-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^*6^*7 + 8) + 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 + 3 - (-2 + 1)$
9729	16593	$-1234 + 5 - 67^*(-89 - AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - 43 - 2 - 1$
972A	16594	$-1^*2^*(-3 + 4 - (5678 - 9A^*B))$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 - 3^* - 2^*1$
972B	16595	$((1 - 2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 - 5^*6)^*7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - (5 + 43 + 2 - 1)$
9730	16596	$((1 - 2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 - 5^*6)^* - 7^*(8 - 9) + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 + 3 - 21$
9731	16597	$1^{\wedge} 2^*(3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 + (-6 - (7 + 8))^*9 - (A + B)$	$-BA + 9876 - (5 + 43 - 2 + 1)$
9732	16598	$1^*(23 + 45 + 6)^*(78 - 9^* - A + B)$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 - 21$
9733	16599	$-1 + 2^*345^*6 - (7 - 89)^*A^*B$	$-BA - (-9876 - (-5 - 43)) - (-2 - 1)$
9734	16600	$-1 - 2 - 34^* - 56 - 7 - 89A^* - B$	$B + A + (-9 + (-8 - 7^*6)^*5)^* - 4^{\wedge} 3 + 2 + 1$
9735	16601	$(-1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5 * 6^7 + 8 - 9 - (A - B))$	$-B - A + 98 + 7^*6^*(-54 + 321)$
9736	16602	$1 - 2 + 34^*56 - 7 - 89A^* - B$	$-B + A + 9876 - (-54^* - 3 - 2) - 1$
9737	16603	$-1 - 2^*(3 - 4)^*(5 + 6 - 78^* - 9^*A + B)$	$-B + A + 9876 - 54^*3 - 2^* - 1$
9738	16604	$1 - 23^* - 45 - 67 + 89AB$	$BA9 - (-8765 - 4 - 3 + 21)$
9739	16605	$-1 - 23 + 4^* - 5 + (6 + 7)^*(89A + B)$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 - 43 - 2 + 1$
973A	16606	$1^*(-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + 9876 - (-54^* - 3 - 21)$
973B	16607	$1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 - 43 + 2 - 1$
9740	16608	$(1 - 2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7)/(8 + 9) + A + B)$	$-BA - (-9876 - 5 + 43 + 2^* - 1)$
9741	16609	$1 + (-2 - 3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^*7)^*(8 + 9) + A - B$	$BA9 + 8^*(7 - 65^*4^* - 3)^*2^*1$
9742	16610	$1234 + 567 - 89^* - AB$	$-B^*(-A - 987 - 65 + 4 - 3 - 21)$
9743	16611	$-1 + 2 - (34^* - 56^*7 - (-8 - 9)^* - A^* - B)$	$B + A + (-9^* - 8^* - 7 + 6^*5)^*(-4^*3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
9744	16612	$-1 - (2^{\wedge} (3^*4 + 5) - 6)/(-7 - 8/9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 + 4 - 32 - 1$
9745	16613	$((1 - 2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 - 5^*6)^*7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3^*2 + 1$
9746	16614	$-1^* - 2^*(-3 + 456)^*(-7 - (-8 + 9) - (-A - B))$	$BA9 - (-8765 - (-4 - 3) - (-2 + 1))$
9747	16615	$123 + 4 - 5 + (-6 - 7)^*(-89 - A)^*B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 21$
9748	16616	$-1 - 23^*4^* - 5^*6 + 789A + B$	$BA9 - (-8765 + 4 + 3) - (-2 + 1)$
9749	16617	$12 + 34^*56 - 7 + 89A^*B$	$BA9 + 8765 - (-4 - 3^*(-2 - 1))$
974A	16618	$12^*(3 + 4 + 56 + 789 - A + B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 + 2 + 1$
974B	16619	$(-1 + (-2 + 3^4)^5) * 6^7 + 8^*9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 - (3^*2 + 1)$
9750	16620	$1 + 2 + (3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 + (-6 - (7 + 8))^*9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9876 + 54^* - 3 - (2 + 1)$
9751	16621	$1^*2 - 3^*(4 + (-5 - 6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - 43 + 21$
9752	16622	$-1 - 2 - 3^*(4 + 56^* - 7) + 89AB$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
9753	16623	$1 - (-2 + (-3 + 4^* - 5^*6)^*(7 + 8))^*9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 + (-3 - 2)^* - 1$
9754	16624	$1 - 2^*((-3 - (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + 7))^*8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - (-5 - 4) - 32 + 1$
9755	16625	$(-1 - 2^*3^4)/-5^*(6 - 7^* - 8^*9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - (-5 - (-4 - 3)) - 21$
9756	16626	$1 - 2^*(3 + (-4^{\wedge} 5 - 6 - 7)^*8 - 9) + A + B$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 - 3 + 2 + 1$
9757	16627	$1^{\wedge} 2 + (-3 + 4^* - 5^*6)^*(-7 - 8)^*9 + A + B$	$-BA - (-9876 + 54) - (-32 - 1)$
9758	16628	$1^*(-2 + 3^4)^5 * -5^* - 6^*7 + 8 + 9 + A + B$	$-B - A^* - 9^*87^*(6 - 5) + 4321$
9759	16629	$-1^*2 + (-3^*(-4 - 5) + 6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 + 4 + 3 - 21$
975A	16630	$-1 + (-2 + 3 - 4 - 5^*6)^* - 7^*8^*9 + A - B$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1$
975B	16631	$(-1 - 2^*3 + 4 - 5^*6)^* - 7^*8^*9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 - 43 + 21$
9760	16632	$12^*(3 - 45 - 6 + 789 + AB)$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 + 3^*2^*1$
9761	16633	$12345 + 67^* - 89 + AB$	$-BA9 - (-8765 - 4) + 3^*2 + 1$
9762	16634	$1 + 2 + (-3^*(-4 - 5) + 6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9 + A - B$	$-BA9 - 87 - 6^*5^*(-432 - 1)$
9763	16635	$1 + 2 + (-3^*(-4 - 5) + 6)^* - 7^* - 8^*9 - (A - B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4^*3 + 21$
9764	16636	$1 - 2^*(-3 - (4^{\wedge} 5 + (-6 - 7)^*8))^*9 + A + B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5^* - 4 + 3 + 2 - 1$
9765	16637	$-1^* - 2^*(3 - (-4^{\wedge} 5 - (6 + 7)^*8) + 9) + A + B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5^*(-4 + 3 - 2^*1)$
9766	16638	$(-1 + 2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4^* - 5^*(-6 - 7) + 8 - 9 + A + B$	$-BA - (-9876 + 5^*4) - 3^*2^* - 1$
9767	16639	$-1 + 2^*34^*(-56 + 78)^*(9A - B)$	$B - (A - 9876 + 5) - 4^*32 + 1$
9768	16640	$-1^*(-23 - 45)^*(-6 - 7)^*(-8 - 9 - A + B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 - 3 + 21$
9769	16641	$1 + 23 + 45 + 6^* - 78^*(-9 - A - B)$	$BA + 9876 + 5 + 4^*3^* - 21$
976A	16642	$(-1 + 2)^*(-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^*7)^*(8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B - (-A - 9876 - 5) + 4^*(-32 - 1)$
976B	16643	$-1 + 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^*7)^*(8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B^*(-A98 + 76 - (5 + 4 - 32^* - 1))$
9770	16644	$-12 + 345^*6 - 7 - 89^* - AB$	$-BA - (-9876 + 5 + 4) - (-3 + 2^*1)$
9771	16645	$1 + 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^*7)^*(8 + 9) + A - B$	$-BA - (-9876 + 5 - (4 - 3^* - 2^* - 1))$
9772	16646	$-123 - 4 - (56 + 7^*89)^*(-A - B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4^*3^* - 2^*1$
9773	16647	$-123 + 45^*6^* - 7^*8 - 9^* - A^* - B$	$-BA + 9876 - (5 - 4 + 3) - (2 - 1)$
9774	16648	$1^*2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + 7)^*8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA9 - (-8765 - 43) - 21$
9775	16649	$1 - 2^{\wedge} 3^* - 4^* - 5^*(-6 - 7)^*8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 - (4 + 3) - 2 + 1$
9776	16650	$1 + (-2^{\wedge} 3^* - 4 + 5)^*(-6 + 7^*8)^*9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 + 4 - 3 + 2^*1$
9777	16651	$1 + 23^* - 4 + (-567 - 8 + 9)^*(-A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 - (-5 + 4 + 3 - 2 + 1)$
9778	16652	$1234 + 56^*(78 - (-9A - B))$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - 4^*(-3 + 2) + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9779	16653	$(-1-2^*3+4-5^*6)^*-7^*8^*9+A+B$	$-BA+9876-(-5+4-3+2)-1$
977A	16654	$(-1-2^*(3-4^*5)+6^*7)^*8-9+A-B$	$BA9+8765-(-4-3-21)$
977B	16655	$1-2+34^*-5^*-67-8^*(-9A+B)$	$BA98-7-65^*43+21$
9780	16656	$-1^*-2^*3^*4^*(567-89)^*(-A+B)$	$BA-(-9876-5^*-43)-21$
9781	16657	$-12+3456+78^*9A-B$	$BA9+8765-4+32+1$
9782	16658	$1+2^*((3+4^*5+6+7)^*8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876)-5-4^*-32^*-1$
9783	16659	$1^*2+3^*(4+5)-6^*7^*8^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876)-(-5+4^*32-1)$
9784	16660	$-123+4^*5^*67+89AB$	$-BA-(-9876-5^*-4)-(-3-21)$
9785	16661	$1+2+3^*(4+5)-6^*7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5+4-3+2+1$
9786	16662	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$-BA9-8-7+6^*-5^*(-432+1)$
9787	16663	$1-234+5+67^*(89A+B)$	$BA9+8765+4+32-1$
9788	16664	$(1+2+3+4)^*5/6+(-7-8)/9+A-B$	$BA9+8765+4-32^*-1$
9789	16665	$1+2+(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA9+8765+4+32+1$
978A	16666	$1^*2-((-3-4)^*5+6-(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-65^*(43-21)$
978B	16667	$12345+6^*(78-9AB)$	$-BA+9876+5+4-3^*-2^*1$
9790	16668	$-1-2+3456+78^*9A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5^*-4+3)-2+1$
9791	16669	$1-23+45^*(67-(-89-AB))$	$BA98+7-65^*43+21$
9792	16670	$1-2+3456-(78^*-9A+B)$	$-B-A-(-9876-(-54-32)+1)$
9793	16671	$(-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^*6+7)^*8/9+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-54+32^*-1$
9794	16672	$-1+2-(-3456-78^*9A+B)$	$BA9+8765+43-2+1$
9795	16673	$1^*2+3456-78^*-9A-B$	$-BA+9876-5+43-21$
9796	16674	$1+2-(-3456-78^*9A+B)$	$BA9+8765+43+2-1$
9797	16675	$-1^*2+(3+4)^*5+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5-4-(-3-21)$
9798	16676	$-1^*2^*(-34-5678+9A^*-B)$	$-BA+9876-(-5-4-3)^*2^*1$
9799	16677	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+54-32-1$
979A	16678	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-54+32^*1)$
979B	16679	$-12+3456-78^*-9A+B$	$-BA+9876+54-32+1$
97A0	16680	$1-(-2+3)-4^*-5^*(6+7^*8^*9+(-A+B))$	$-BA+9876-(-5+4-32+1)$
97A1	16681	$1+2-3+456^*(-78+9A)-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5+4-3-21)$
97A2	16682	$1+23^*45+6-7+89AB$	$-BA+9876-5-4+32+1$
97A3	16683	$1^*2-((-3-4)^*5+6)-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5-43+21)$
97A4	16684	$-1-(2^*3+(-4^*5+6^*7)^*(8+9))+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-5+4^*-3)+21$
97A5	16685	$12+3456-(-78^*9A+B)$	$-B+A+9876-(-5-43^*-2)-1$
97A6	16686	$(1+2+3+4)^*5/6+(-7-8)/9+A+B$	$BA+9876-5^*(43-2+1)$
97A7	16687	$1+2^*3+4^*-5^*(-678-9A+B)$	$B^*(-A+987-(-65-43))^*(2-1)$
97A8	16688	$12^*(3+4-(-5+67-89A+B))$	$B-(-A987-65^*(-43+21))$
97A9	16689	$12-34^*(-56-7)+89^*AB$	$-BA-(-9876-5)+4+3+21$
97AA	16690	$-1-(2-3456-78^*9A-B)$	$-BA+9876-5+4+32+1$
97AB	16691	$1-2+(3+4)^*5-6^*7-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876^*(5-4)+32+1$
97B0	16692	$1-2+3456+78^*9A+B$	$-B+A-(-9876-(-54-32))+1$
97B1	16693	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6^*7-8^*9+A-B$	$BA9+8765-4+3^*21$
97B2	16694	$-1+2^*3^*(4+56)^*7+89^*AB$	$-BA-(-9876-54-32+1)$
97B3	16695	$-12+34^*567-89AB$	$B+A+9876+5^*-4^*3^*-2^*-1$
97B4	16696	$-1-2^*3+456^*(-78+9A)+B$	$-BA+9876-5+43-2^*1$
97B5	16697	$1+2+(3+4)^*5-6^*7-8^*9-(-A-B)$	$-BA+9876-5+43-2+1$
97B6	16698	$1234+5^*-6+(-7-89)^*-AB$	$BA9+8765-(-43-21)$
97B7	16699	$-1^*(-2^*3+(-4^*5+6^*7)^*(8+9))+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876-5+4+3^*21)$
97B8	16700	$-1+2+3456+(-78-9)^*AB$	$-BA+9876-5+43-2^*-1$
97B9	16701	$-1-23^*(-4-5)^*6-7+89AB$	$-BA+9876-(-5-(43+2)-1)$
97BA	16702	$1+2^*-34^*5^*6^*-7-(-8+9-A)^*-B$	$-B-A+9876+5-43-21$
97BB	16703	$1-234+5^*(67-89)^*-AB$	$-B-A-(-9876+54)-(-3+2)-1$
9800	16704	$1+2^*(-3-4^*5^*6+7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-54+3+2^*1)$
9801	16705	$-1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$-BA9-(-8-7)-(-6^*-5^*-432+1)$
9802	16706	$-1-2+34^*567-89AB$	$-BA9-(-8-7)-6^*-5^*-432^*-1$
9803	16707	$12-(-3456+78^*-9A)+B$	$-BA+9876+54-3^*(2+1)$
9804	16708	$1-(2+34^*-567+89AB)$	$-BA9+8-7-6^*5^*432^*-1$
9805	16709	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876-5-43-2)-1$
9806	16710	$-1+2+34^*567-89AB$	$BA9+8765+4^*(-3+21)$
9807	16711	$1+(-2+3+4^*5-6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5^*-4^*3-(-2-1)$
9808	16712	$12-(-3+45^*(-67-(89+AB)))$	$-B+A-(-9876+5)-(-43+21)$
9809	16713	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5+(-6-7)^*8+9A-B$	$B+A+9876-54-32^*1$
980A	16714	$-1+2+3+(-4-(5+6))^*(-789+A-B)$	$-BA+9876+54-(3-(-2-1))$
980B	16715	$12345-6^*7-8^*9^*A^*B$	$-B-A-(-9876-(-54+3))-2+1$
9810	16716	$12^*(-3-45+6+789+AB)$	$-BA+9876+54+3-2-1$
9811	16717	$1+2^*(3+4)^*(5+67-8^*(-9-AB))$	$-BA+9876+54-(-3-2)^*-1$
9812	16718	$-1-23-456-78^*-9^*(A+B)$	$-BA+9876+54+3-2+1$
9813	16719	$-1^*(23+456-78^*-9^*(-A-B))$	$BA+9876-54^*3-21$
9814	16720	$1^*(-23-45)^*(-67-8+9-AB)$	$-B^*(-A98-7+6+5+4+3+21)$
9815	16721	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5-6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+54+3+2^*1$
9816	16722	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-(-54-(-3+2))+1$
9817	16723	$12+34^*567-89AB$	$B+A+9876-54-3-21$
9818	16724	$1+2+(3+4)^*5-6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876-5+43)-(-2+1)$
9819	16725	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8765-4^*-321$
981A	16726	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876+5)-(-43-2))+1$
981B	16727	$((1+2^*3)^*4+5-6)^*7-8^*9+A-B$	$B-A+9876-(-54+3)-(-2-1)$
9820	16728	$1+2+(3+4)^*5-6^*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5-(-4+3^*-21)$
9821	16729	$-1+23-456^*(78-9A)+B$	$B-A-9+8765+4^*321$
9822	16730	$-1-2+(3+4)^*5+6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6-54)^*(-3-21)$
9823	16731	$1^*(234-567-89^*A)^*-B$	$B+A+9876-5-4+3^*-21$
9824	16732	$1-2+(3+4)^*5+6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5^*4^*(-3-2+1)$
9825	16733	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5+6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876+5+43+21$
9826	16734	$1-(-23-45-(6+7)^*(89A+B))$	$B-(-A-9876-(-5-43)+21)$
9827	16735	$1+(2^*3+4+5)^*6/7-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-5+4-32+1$
9828	16736	$1+2+(3+4)^*5+6-7-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-(-5+4+3+21)$
9829	16737	$1^*2+(3+4)^*5-6+7-8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-54+3+21$
982A	16738	$1+2+(-34+5)^*-67+89A^*B$	$-BA+9876+54-3+21$
982B	16739	$-1+23^*-4^*(56-78-9A-B)$	$-B+A-(-9876+5+43)+2^*1$
9830	16740	$-1^*23^*4^*(56-(78-(-9A-B)))$	$-B+A+9876-5-43+2+1$
9831	16741	$(1+2^*3)^*(4-5+6)+7-8^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876+5)-(-4-3^*-21)$
9832	16742	$-1^*(2-(-3456+7^*89^*A))^*B$	$B^*(A+987+6+5-43^*2^*-1)$
9833	16743	$1^*2^*(3+4)^*5+(-6+7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+65^*(4-3)^*21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9834	16744	12345-6-7+8*-9*A*B	-BA+9876+54+3+21
9835	16745	-1*2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8*9+A-B	-B+A*(-9-8765+4*-321)
9836	16746	1*(-2+3)*-456+78*9*(A+B)	-B-A+9876+5-4-3-21
9837	16747	1^2*(3+4)^5-6*7-8-9+A-B	B-A+9876-(-5+43-2*-1)
9838	16748	1^2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8*9+A-B	B-A+9876-(-5+43)-(2-1)
9839	16749	1*2+(3+4)^5-6*7-8-9+A-B	-BA-(-9876+5-43*2*1)
983A	16750	1+2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8*9+A-B	B-A-9*(-876-5-432)*1
983B	16751	-1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7*8+9+A-B	B+A+9876-54+3-2-1
9840	16752	1-2+(3+4)^5-6-7*8+9+A-B	-B-(A-9876-5+43-21)
9841	16753	1+23*-45+(-67-8)*(-9-A)*B	B-A+9876-54-3+21
9842	16754	1*-2*(34-5678+9*AB)	-B-A-(-9876+5*-4+32)-1
9843	16755	1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7*8+9+A-B	-BA+9876+54+32+1
9844	16756	12345+6-7+8*9*A*-B	B-(A-9876+5-4-32*-1)
9845	16757	12-3-456+78*-9*(-A-B)	-B-A+9876+5+4*(-3-2)-1
9846	16758	12*(-3-4+5+6*7+8+9)*(A+B)	B+A+9876-(-5*-4+32-1)
9847	16759	1-2*(3+4)*(5+67-89A-B)	B-A+9876-(54-(3+21))
9848	16760	1-(2+3*45*(-6-78)-9*AB)	-B-A+9876+5+4+3-21
9849	16761	-1*2+(3+4)^5-6*7+8-9+A-B	B+A-9*(-876-5-432+1)
984A	16762	1-23*-45+67+89AB	-B-(-A-9876+5)-(43-21)
984B	16763	12+3-456-78*-9*(A+B)	-B+A+9876-(5-4*-3*2)-1
9850	16764	1*-2*(3+4*5-6-(7*-89-A))*-B	-BA+9876-(5+43)*-2*1
9851	16765	1*2+(3+4)^5-6*7+8-9+A-B	-B+A+9876-(-5-4+32-1)
9852	16766	1+2+(3+4)^5-6*7+8-9+A-B	-B+A+9876-54+32-1
9853	16767	-1-2-3*-4+(567+8-9)*(A+B)	B-A+9876+5+4-32+1
9854	16768	1*(234-56)*(-7-(8*-9-A+B))	B+A+9876-5-4+32*-1
9855	16769	1-(2-(3+4)^5)-6*(7+8-9)+A-B	BA+9876+54*-3+21
9856	16770	12345+6-(-7+8*-9*A*-B)	BA9-(-8765+4*(-32+1))
9857	16771	-1-23*(4+56+7)*8-(-9-AB)	B-(-A-9876)-(-5+43)+2*1
9858	16772	12*(-3-4-56+78+9*AB)	B+A+9876+5-43+2+1
9859	16773	-1-2+(3+4)^5-6-7-8-9+A-B	BA+9876+5*-4*-3*2+1
985A	16774	1+23-456+78*9*(A+B)	-BA+9876-5-4*32*-1
985B	16775	-1*(234-56-(7-89A))*-B	B+A+9876-5+4-32-1
9860	16776	1^2*(3+4)^5-6-7-8-9+A-B	B+A-(-9876+5-4+32*1)
9861	16777	-1+2-(34*-5*67+8*(9-AB))	B+A+9876-5-(-4+32-1)
9862	16778	1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7-8-9+A-B	BA+9876-5+43*(-2-1)
9863	16779	12-3+4*(-56-(7-89))*AB	B+A+9876+5-4-32+1
9864	16780	-123+4*567+89*AB	-B-(-A-9876-5-4-(3+2)))+1
9865	16781	(1^2*3+4)^5-6*7+8+9+A-B	-B-A+9876-(5*4-3)+21
9866	16782	1^2+(3+4)^5-6*7+8+9+A-B	-B+A+9876-(-54+3*21)
9867	16783	1*2+(3+4)^5-6*7+8+9+A-B	BA-(-9876+5+4*(32-1))
9868	16784	123+45-6*78*(-9-(A+B))	B-A+9876+5+4*3*-21
9869	16785	-1-2+(3+4)^5+6-7-8-9+A-B	-B+A+9876-5-4+3-2*1
986A	16786	-12*(-3+4-(-56+7)-(89A-B))	-B-A+9876-(5*-4-3*-2+1)
986B	16787	1-2+(3+4)^5+6-7-8-9+A-B	B+A+9876+5+4-(32-1)
9870	16788	1^2*(3+4)^5+6-7-8-9+A-B	B-A+9876-(5-4+3*-2*-1)
9871	16789	(1+2+3-4+5)^6/7-8-9+A-B	B-A-(-9876+5-4+3)+2*-1
9872	16790	1+(2*3-4+5)^6/7-8-9+A-B	BA+9876+5-4*32+1
9873	16791	1-2+(3+4)^5-6-7+8-9+A-B	-BA+9876+5+4-3*-21
9874	16792	123-4*-56*7*(8-(9-A))-B	-B-(A-9876-5)-(-4+3))+21
9875	16793	1-2+(3+4)^5-6-7-8+9+A-B	BA+9876+5+4*(-32+1)
9876	16794	1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7+8-9+A-B	B-(-A-9876-(5-43+21))
9877	16795	1+2+(3+4)^5-6-7+8-9+A-B	B-A+9876-54*(-3+21)
9878	16796	1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7-8+9+A-B	B-A+9876-(-5+4-(3-2))-1
9879	16797	1+2+(3+4)^5-6-7-8+9+A-B	B-(A-9876-5)-(-4-(3+2))*-1
987A	16798	-12-3*4*(-56+78-9AB)	-B+A+9876+5+4-3-2+1
987B	16799	1+2-(3-456-7)*(-89+AB)	B-A+9876-5+4+3+2*1
9880	16800	12*3*4*(-5+67-89+AB)	-B-A+9876+54-32+1
9881	16801	1-2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8-9+A-B	B+A-(-9876+5+4+3-2*-1)
9882	16802	1^2*(3+4)^5+6+7-8-9+A-B	B-(A-9876)+5-4+3+2+1
9883	16803	12+34*(56-7-8-9)*A-B	-B-A-(-9876-(-5-4+32+1))
9884	16804	1-2+34-5*(6+7)*(-8+9A)*B	-B+A+9876-54-3*-21
9885	16805	1-23+4*-5*-67+89AB	B+A+9876-5+4*(-3+2)-1
9886	16806	1+(2^3+4-5)^6/7+8-9+A-B	B-(A-9876)-54+3*21
9887	16807	(1+2+3-4+5)^6/7-8+9+A-B	-B-A987-65*(-4-321)
9888	16808	1+23*(456-(7+8))+9-AB	-BA+9876+5+4*32-1
9889	16809	1+2+(3+4)^5-6+7+8-9+A-B	-BA+9876+5-4*-32*1
988A	16810	-1234+56*(-78+9A)*B	B+A+9876-5-4+3+2-1
988B	16811	1+2+(3+4)^5-6+7-8+9+A-B	-B-(A-9876)-(-5-4-32-1)
9890	16812	1*2+(3+4)^5-6-7+8+9+A-B	B+A+9876-5+4-3+2-1
9891	16813	-1+2+3*4*(56-78+9AB)	B-A+9876-5*4+32*1
9892	16814	-12-(3-4*5*67-89AB)	-B+A+9876-5+4-3+21
9893	16815	-1-2+(3+4)^5+6+7+8-9+A-B	-B-A-(-9876-54)-(-3+21)
9894	16816	1+2345-6-78*(-9-AB)	B-A+9876-5+43-21
9895	16817	-1-2-3+45-(-6-7)*(-8-9A*-B)	-B-A-(-9876+5-43+2*1)
9896	16818	1^2*(3+4)^5+6+7+8-9+A-B	-B+A+9876+54-32-1
9897	16819	1-2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8+9+A-B	-B*(-A-987-65-4-32-1)
9898	16820	-12+3-4*-5*67+89AB	-B+A+9876-5+4-(-3-21)
9899	16821	1*-23*(-456-7-89+AB)	B-A+9876+54+32*-1
989A	16822	1*2+(3+4)^5+6+7-8+9+A-B	B-(A-9876-(54-32)-1)
989B	16823	1+23*(456-(7+8))-9A+B	-B+A+9876-5-4+32+1
98A0	16824	1+(2^3+4-5)^6/7+8+9+A-B	-B+A+9876-(-5-43+21)
98A1	16825	1234+567-89A*-B	BA+9876-(-5-43)*-2+1
98A2	16826	1*2+(3+4)^5-6+7+8+9+A-B	B+A+9876-54+3*21
98A3	16827	1*2345+6-78*(-9-AB)	-B-A-(-9876-5-43)+2*-1
98A4	16828	1*(-2-3-(4+5))*(-67-89A-B)	-B-A+9876+5+43-2+1
98A5	16829	-1*2+(3+4)^5+6*7-8-9+A-B	-B+A987-6-5-4*321
98A6	16830	-1*(-2-3-45+6-78-9)*A*B	B*(A98+7-6-(-5+4+3+21))
98A7	16831	12345-6-7*8*(9+AB)	B-A-(-9876-54)-(-3+21)
98A8	16832	-1*2*(-3+4-5678+9*AB)	B-A+9876-(-5-4-(3+21))
98A9	16833	1*2+(3+4)^5+6*7-8-9+A-B	-B+A+9876+5-4+32+1
98AA	16834	-1+2*(-3-4+567)+89AB	B+A+9876-(-5+4-3-21)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
98AB	16835	$-1+2+34+(-5-6-7)*(-8*9A+B)$	$B+A+9876-5-4*-3*2+1$
98B0	16836	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-5+43-21$
98B1	16837	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7+8*9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-54)-(-3+21)$
98B2	16838	$-12+345-(-6-7)*(89A-B)$	$-B+A-(-9876+5-43+2-1)$
98B3	16839	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A-(-9876-54-3+2-1)$
98B4	16840	$((1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876-5+43+2-1$
98B5	16841	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B-A+9876+5+4+32-1$
98B6	16842	$-12*(34-5+6-(789+AB))$	$B-(-A-9876-54)-(32-1)$
98B7	16843	$1-2*-3*-4*-56+7+89AB$	$B-A-(-9876-5-4-32)+1$
98B8	16844	$-1*-2*(-3+4-5-67*-89+AB)$	$BA+9876-54-(3+21)$
98B9	16845	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A-(-9876-(-5-4+32+1))$
98BA	16846	$-1+2*(3+4567)-8+9AB$	$B+A+9876-(-5-43)-21$
98BB	16847	$-12+34*5*-67-89*-A+B$	$-BA+9876-54*3-(-2-1)$
9900	16848	$-1*-23*(4-567-8+9AB)$	$B-A+9876+5+43-2-1$
9901	16849	$-1+2+3*(4+5)*6*(78-9+A+B)$	$-BA-98*7*-6*5-4321$
9902	16850	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8-9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876+54-3)-21$
9903	16851	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7-8+9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876-(-54+3*-2*-1)$
9904	16852	$1+23*(45+6)+7+89AB$	$B-A98-(-7+6*-5*(432-1))$
9905	16853	$1-2-3*45*(-6+7)*(-89-(-A+B))$	$B-A-(-9876-54+3+2+1)$
9906	16854	$-1*2*-3*-45*(-67-89+AB)$	$B-A+9876+5+43+2+1$
9907	16855	$1234+56*-7+89AB$	$BA+9876-5-43-21$
9908	16856	$-12*(-3-45*-6-(78+9AB))$	$B-A+9876+54+3*(-2+1)$
9909	16857	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-54)-3+2-1$
990A	16858	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-5+43-2-1$
990B	16859	$1-(-23+4*-5*67-89AB)$	$B-A+9876-(-54+3)+2+1$
9910	16860	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A98+7+6*5*-432*-1$
9911	16861	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B-A+9876-5-4-3*-21$
9912	16862	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876+54+3+2*1$
9913	16863	$-1-2-34+(56+78)*(9A-B)$	$B-A+9876+54+3+2-1$
9914	16864	$1+2-(34*-5*67-89*A-B)$	$B+A+9876-5+43+2+1$
9915	16865	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7+8+9+A-B$	$BA+9876-(-5-(-43-21))$
9916	16866	$123+45*(67+89+AB)$	$BA-(-9876+54)-(-3+2+1)$
9917	16867	$1*(-2-3-(4+56+78))*(-9*A-B)$	$B-A98-7+6*5*432-1$
9918	16868	$-12+3*45*(6+78+9)-AB$	$BA+9876-(-54-(-3-(-2-1)))$
9919	16869	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$B-A+9876-5+4+3*21$
991A	16870	$-12*(34+5-(6+789+AB))$	$BA+9876-54-3+2-1$
991B	16871	$((1+2*3)^{\wedge}4+5-6)*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876-(-54+3)+2*1$
9920	16872	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876-5-43-2)-1$
9921	16873	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA+9876-54*(3-2)+1$
9922	16874	$123+456*(-78+9A)+B$	$B-(-A-9876+5-43)-(-2-1)$
9923	16875	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-54+32*-1)$
9924	16876	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-5-(43+21))$
9925	16877	$-1-234*-5-6-7+89AB$	$BA-(-9876-(-5-43))-(-2+1)$
9926	16878	$(1-2+3-4-5)^{\wedge}6/7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9876+54-(-3+2*-1)$
9927	16879	$1-234*-5-(6+7)+89AB$	$BA+9876-5-43-(-2-1)$
9928	16880	$-1*-2*-34*(5-67-8-9A-B)$	$B+A+9876+54*(3-2)+1$
9929	16881	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-54+3)+21$
992A	16882	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876+5*-43)-21$
992B	16883	$((1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5+6)*7/(-8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9876-5-43+2+1$
9930	16884	$1*-2*(3+4)*(5-(-67-(8+9A*-B)))$	$B-(-A-9876-54)+3-2*-1$
9931	16885	$12-3-(-456+7)*(89-AB)$	$-B+A+9876+54+3+21$
9932	16886	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+(-6+7+8)*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876-5)+4*(-3+21)$
9933	16887	$12+345*6-7+89A*B$	$B-A-(-9876-54-(3+21))$
9934	16888	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7+8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876-5-4-32-1$
9935	16889	$-1+234*5-(-6+7-89AB)$	$-B+A-(-9876+5)-43*-2-1$
9936	16890	$-1-234*-5+(-6+7)*89AB$	$BA+9876-5-4-32+1$
9937	16891	$-1-234*-5-6+7+89AB$	$BA+9876+5-43+2-1$
9938	16892	$12+34*-5*-67-(8-9*-A)*-B$	$BA+9876+5-(43-2*1)$
9939	16893	$-12-3+4-(56+78)*(-9A+B)$	$BA-(-9876-5+43-2)+1$
993A	16894	$12-3*-45*(6+78)+9A*B$	$B+A+9876-54-(3-21)$
993B	16895	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*4)*(-5+6-(7-8))^{\wedge}9+A-B$	$-B+A+9876+54+32*1$
9940	16896	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876)+54-(-32+1)$
9941	16897	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7+8*9+A+B$	$BA98-7+6*(5-432-1)$
9942	16898	$-1+(-2-3)*(4+(-5-6*7)*8*9)+A-B$	$BA*(-9-(-8-76))-5-4+32+1$
9943	16899	$-1-234+(56+7)*(89+AB)$	$BA+9876-(-5+4+3+21)$
9944	16900	$1234+5+(-67+8)*(9A)*-B$	$BA+9876-54+3+21$
9945	16901	$-1+2*3+4*-56*(7+8*-9-A+B)$	$B-(-A-9876)+54-(3-21)$
9946	16902	$-1-2+3-4-(56+78)*(-9A+B)$	$-BA+9876-5*(-43-(-2+1))$
9947	16903	$-12-3+4*5*6*(-7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A+9876-5*(-43+21)$
9948	16904	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+(6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*-43-2-1$
9949	16905	$1-234*-5+6-(-7-89AB)$	$BA+9876-5-43+21$
994A	16906	$-12-34*-5*67-8*(-9-AB)$	$BA-(-9876-5)-(-4+32+1)$
994B	16907	$1*2-((-3-4)^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8))+9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-5-4-32*-1)$
9950	16908	$-1+23*(456-7)-89-AB$	$-BA+9876-(-5*43-2)-1$
9951	16909	$(1-2+3)^{\wedge}4(4*5-6)+7*8*9+A+B$	$BA-(-9876-(-54+32)+1)$
9952	16910	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876-(-54-32*1)$
9953	16911	$1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876-54-(-32-1)$
9954	16912	$1234-5*67+89AB$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-54-3*21)$
9955	16913	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+9876-5-43*-2+1$
9956	16914	$1*2*(34+5678+9*-AB)$	$B-(-A-9876-5*4*3*2)-1$
9957	16915	$1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8+9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5-4+3-21$
9958	16916	$(1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8+9-(-A-B)$	$B-(-A-9876)-(-54-32+1)$
9959	16917	$123-456+78*9*(A+B)$	$-B+A987+65+4*-321$
995A	16918	$-12+3*-4*(-5+6+7+8-9AB)$	$B+A-(-9876-54)-(-32-1)$
995B	16919	$1-23*(4-56)-(-7-89AB)$	$BA+9876-5*-4-(-32-1)$
9960	16920	$-1*2*(-34-5)*(6+7*(-89+AB))$	$-B-(-A-9876-5+4*-32*-1))$
9961	16921	$1-2+3+4*(-56*7-8)*-9-(-A+B)$	$BA-(-9876+5+4+3)-(-2+1)$
9962	16922	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876-(-5-4*3)*2*-1$
9963	16923	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-5)+4+3-21$
9964	16924	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+(6+7)*8-9+A+B$	$B-(-A+9)+8*7*(65*-4-3*2*-1)$
9965	16925	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6-7)*8-9+A+B$	$BA-(-9876-54+3*21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9966	16926	$12^*(34+5-6)*(-7+8+9+A+B)$	$BA+9876-5-4-3+2*1$
9967	16927	$1+(2*3)^4+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876+5)-4-(-3+2+1)$
9968	16928	$-123+4*56*7+89AB$	$BA+9876+5*4-3-21$
9969	16929	$-1*(234-56-(-7-89A))*-B$	$-B*(-A9+87+65*(4+3))*(-2-1)$
996A	16930	$-1-23*(45+67*8)+9A*B$	$B+A-98+(-76+543)*21$
996B	16931	$-12+3456+789*A-B$	$BA-(-9876-5)-4-(3+2+1)$
9970	16932	$-1+234*5+6*7+89AB$	$BA+9876-5-4+3-2*-1$
9971	16933	$(-1+2+(-3-4)*5)*(6-7*8*9)-(A-B)$	$BA+9876-5-4+3+2+1$
9972	16934	$1-(2+(-3-4)^5+6+(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B-A+9876+54-3*-21$
9973	16935	$((-1+2)*3+4)^5-6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9876-5-(-4-3)-(-2+1)$
9974	16936	$1+23*4*(56+78)-9A-B$	$BA+9876+5*4*(3-2-1)$
9975	16937	$-1-23+4*-5+67*(89+A*B)$	$BA+9876+5-4-3-(-2-1)$
9976	16938	$1^2+3^4*5*6*7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+(7+6*5^4+3)^2*1$
9977	16939	$(-1+2*3)*(4+(-5-6*7)*-8*9)+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-5-4)-(3-(-2-1))$
9978	16940	$-12+3-(-4*567+89*-AB)$	$B*(-A9-(-87-65)+4)*(3+21)$
9979	16941	$(1+2*3)^4(4-(-5-6))-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5+4-3-(-2-1)$
997A	16942	$-1-2-(-3456-789*A+B)$	$B-A+9876-5+4*32*1$
997B	16943	$1-2+3*-4*(-5+6)*(7+8-9AB)$	$BA+9876-5-4*3*(-2+1)$
9980	16944	$12+345-(6+7)*(89+A)*-B$	$-BA9-87*6+543*21$
9981	16945	$1+(2*3)^4+5^6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA-9876*(-5+4)-3*(-2-1)$
9982	16946	$123-(4-567*(8-9))*(-A-B)$	$BA+9876+5+(-4-3+2)*-1$
9983	16947	$1-(2+3)+4*567+89*AB$	$BA-(-9876+54-3*21)$
9984	16948	$1^2+(3+4)^5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5+4-3*(-2+1)$
9985	16949	$1-(-2-34-(-56-78))*(-9A+B)$	$BA+9876-5-4-3+21$
9986	16950	$1+2+(3+4)^5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A-(-9876-5)+4*-32*-1$
9987	16951	$(-1-2/3^4-4)*(5-(-6*(-7-8)+9))+A-B$	$BA+9876+5+4-(-3-(2+1))$
9988	16952	$-1*(-23+45)*(67+8*9*-A-B)$	$BA+9876+5+4*3-2+1$
9989	16953	$-12+3456-789*-A+B$	$BA+9876-5*4+32-1$
998A	16954	$12*(-3-4)*5*(67-(8-9A)-B)$	$BA+9876+5*4-3+2-1$
998B	16955	$-1+2+3-4*-567+89*AB$	$BA+9876-5+4*(3+2+1)$
9990	16956	$1*-23*-4*(56+7+89-A-B)$	$BA+9876-5*-4*(3+2*-1)$
9991	16957	$((1+2*3)^4+5+6)*7+8*9-(A-B)$	$BA+9876-(5-43+21)$
9992	16958	$1*(2-3)*(-45-(-6+78))*(-9+AB)$	$BA-9-(-8-76+543)*-21$
9993	16959	$-12-3+4*(5-(-6+7))*(-89*-A+B)$	$BA+9876+5-4-3+21$
9994	16960	$1*(2+3)*-45*(-6*-7-89+A-B)$	$-B+A+9876-54*3-21$
9995	16961	$-1+2*-3*(45-6+78+9A)*-B$	$B-(-A-(9876-5)+4*-32)))-1$
9996	16962	$1-2*(-3+(-4^5-6*7)*8)+9-A*B$	$BA+9876+5*4-(-3-2-1)$
9997	16963	$1+2-3*-4*56*7+8*9AB$	$BA+9876+54-32+1$
9998	16964	$1+2+3-(-45-(-6+78))*(-9+AB)$	$BA+9876-5-4+32-1$
9999	16965	$1+23*(456-7)+8-9*(A+B)$	$BA-(-9876-5+4-3-21)$
999A	16966	$(-1+2-3*-4*-5*-6)*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$B-A+9876-5*(4-32)+1$
999B	16967	$123-4-(-567+8-9)*(A+B)$	$BA+9876+5+4-(-3-21)$
99A0	16968	$-1+2+3456+789*A+B$	$BA+9876-5-(-4*3-21)$
99A1	16969	$-1-234*5-(-67-89AB)$	$BA+9876-5*(-4-3)-2*1$
99A2	16970	$1+2+3456-789*-A+B$	$-B-A-987-6*5*(432-1)$
99A3	16971	$1+234*5+67+89AB$	$BA+9876-5*-4*3-21$
99A4	16972	$-123+4567-8*9*-AB$	$BA+9876+54-3-21$
99A5	16973	$1-23*4*-56+78*(9A-B)$	$BA+9876-5+4-32*-1$
99A6	16974	$12+3*4*56*7+8*9AB$	$BA+9876+5+4+32-1$
99A7	16975	$(-1-2)*((-3-4^5)*6-7*-8*9)-(A-B)$	$BA-(-9876-5+4)-32*-1$
99A8	16976	$(-1-(2+3^4))*(5*6*7+8)+9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-5)-4-(-32-1)$
99A9	16977	$1-(-234+5)-(-6+7)*(-89A-B)$	$B+A+9*(-8-7-6/5^4-4-3)/-2*1$
99AA	16978	$1+2*-3*(-4-5*(6+7*8))*9+A+B$	$BA+9876+54+3-21$
99AB	16979	$1-(23-4*5-67*(89-A*-B))$	$BA+9876-5+43-(2+1)$
99B0	16980	$-1/-2*(3-(4^5-6^7/8+9))+A-B$	$BA+9876-5+43+2*-1$
99B1	16981	$12+3456-(-789*A-B)$	$BA+9876-(5-(43-2))+1$
99B2	16982	$-12*(-3+4-5*-6-789-AB)$	$-B+A-98+76*(-54*-3-2)-1$
99B3	16983	$-1*(234+5)*(67+8+9-AB)$	$BA+9876-5+43+2-1$
99B4	16984	$((1+2+3)^4+5)*(6+7)+8*9+A-B$	$B*(A98-(-7+6)-(-5-4)-(-3+21))$
99B5	16985	$(1+2+3)^4+5^6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B-(-A-9876-54*3-2*-1)$
99B6	16986	$1+(2*3)^4+5^6+7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8*7-6^5/4+3)^2(2-1)$
99B7	16987	$-1-2-34+5*(-67+89)*AB$	$-B+A+9876-54*-3-2*-1$
99B8	16988	$(-1+2-3*-4*-5*-6)*(7*8-9)+A+B$	$-B-(-A-9876)+5*(4-(-32-1))$
99B9	16989	$12+345*(-67-8-9+AB)$	$BA+9876-(-5-43-(-2-1))$
99BA	16990	$1-2+(-3^4(4-(-5-6))+7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B-A+9876-54*3-(-2-1)$
99BB	16991	$((1+2)^(3-4)^5+6-7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5+43-2+1$
99A00	16992	$1^2*3^4*5*6*7-8-9+A-B$	$B-A-98*7*6*5-4321$
99A01	16993	$1^2+3^4*5*6*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5*4-(-32+1)$
99A02	16994	$12-3*4*(5+6-7+8-9AB)$	$BA+9876+5-(-43-2*1)$
99A03	16995	$-123-4*-567+89A*B$	$BA+9876-(-5-43-2-1)$
99A04	16996	$-12-34*5*67+(8-9A)*-B$	$BA-(-9876-54-(-3-2+1))$
99A05	16997	$1*2+(3+4)^5-(-6-(7+8))*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8/7+6)*(-5*(-4-3))^2+1$
99A06	16998	$-1-23-4-5*(67-89)*AB$	$BA+9876+54-3+2-1$
99A07	16999	$12+3*-45*(6-7-89)+AB$	$BA+9876-(-54+3)-2*-1$
99A08	17000	$1+(2*3)^4+5^6+7+8*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+54-3+2+1$
99A09	17001	$-1-2-3*-4*(-5-6-(7-8-9AB))$	$-B-A+(9+((-8-7)/6)^5)/-4^4-3*(2+1)$
99A0A	17002	$-1/-2*(3-(4^5-6^7/8+9))+A+B$	$BA+9876-(-54-3)-(-2-1)$
99A0B	17003	$-1+234*5-67*(-89-AB)$	$BA+9876+54-3*(-2+1)$
99A10	17004	$(1+2)^3*(4+(-5-6)*-7*8+9)+A+B$	$BA+9876+54+3+2-1$
99A11	17005	$-1+(-2+3^4)*-5*(-6*7+8-9)+A+B$	$BA9-8+76*5*(4-32)*-1$
99A12	17006	$12-3*-4-5-67*(-89+A*-B)$	$-B*(-A98-(7-6-(-54+3*21)))$
99A13	17007	$1-2+3^4*5*6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876-5+43+21$
99A14	17008	$1-23+4+5*(-67+89)*AB$	$-BA9-8*76*(-54+32)+1$
99A15	17009	$1^2+3^4*5*6*7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8)*7-6+5^4*3^4(2+1)$
99A16	17010	$-1*(2+3+4-(-56+7-89))*(-A-B)$	$BA+9876-5+4+3*21$
99A17	17011	$1+2+3^4*5*6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA-9876*(-5+4)-3*-21$
99A18	17012	$(-1-(2-3^4))*(-5*-6*7+8)+9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5-4-3*-21$
99A19	17013	$1+2+3^4*5*6*7-8+9+A-B$	$BA9-87*-65+4321$
99A1A	17014	$1+23*(456-7)+8-(9+AB)$	$B+A+9*(-8*7+6^5/4)^(-3-2)+1$
99A1B	17015	$((1+2*3)^4+5*6)*7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9^8(8-7)*(6+5^4)*3-2+1$
99A20	17016	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5+6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$-BA-9+8*(765-4*3)*2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9A21	17017	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)) * (5 - (6 + (-7-8) * 9)) + A - B$	$BA + 9876 - (-5 - (43 + 21))$
9A22	17018	$12 - 3 * -4 * (-5 - (6 + 7)) - (-8 - 9AB)$	$B + A * (9 + 8) / (7 - 6 + 5 + 4) ^{\wedge} - 3 - (2 + 1)$
9A23	17019	$1 * 2 + (3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 - (-6 - (7 + 8)) * 9 + A + B$	$-BA - 98 + 76 * 54 * 3 - 2 - 1$
9A24	17020	$((1 + 2) ^{\wedge} (3 + 4) - (-5 * 6 + 7) * 8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA + 9876 + 5 - (-4 - 3 * 21)$
9A25	17021	$(1 + 2 + 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A + B$	$B - A * (-9 - (-8 + 765 + 432 + 1))$
9A26	17022	$1 + (2 * 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6 + 7 + 8 * 9 + A + B$	$BA + 9876 + 54 - 3 + 21$
9A27	17023	$1 - 2 + (3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 + 6 * 7 * 8 - 9 - A * B$	$-B - (-A - 9876) - (5 * -43 + 21)$
9A28	17024	$-12 * (3 - (-45 - (-6 - 7 - 89A + B)))$	$-B - A * (-9 + 8) + (76 - 543) * -21$
9A29	17025	$1 - 23 * (-456 + 7) + (8 - 9 - A) * B$	$B - (A + 9 - 8) - (76 - 543) * 21$
9A2A	17026	$12345 - 6 * (7 + 89A) + B$	$B + A - 9 * (8 - 7 * (6 + 5)) + 4 ^{\wedge} (3 * 2 + 1)$
9A2B	17027	$1 ^{\wedge} 2 + 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - 9 * (-8 + 7 + (-6 - 5 ^{\wedge} 4) * 3) + 2 * 1$
9A30	17028	$1 * -2 * (3 * 4 - 5 + 67) * (-8 + 9 - A) * B$	$BA + 9876 + 54 + 3 + 21$
9A31	17029	$12345 - 678 * (9 + A - B)$	$B + A + 9 * (-8 + 7 + 6 + 5 ^{\wedge} 4) * 3 - 2 ^{\wedge} 1$
9A32	17030	$-1 * (-2 - (-3 - 45 + 67 + 89)) * AB$	$-B - A + 9876 + 5 * 43 - 2 * -1$
9A33	17031	$1 + 2 + 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$-B - A + 9876 + 5 * 43 + 2 + 1$
9A34	17032	$1 - (-2 - 3 + 4 + 5 * (67 - 89) * AB)$	$B - (-A - 9876) - (-54 * 3 - 21)$
9A35	17033	$((1 + 2 * 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6) * 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9876 - 5 - 43 * 2 * -1$
9A36	17034	$12 + 34 - 5 - 67 * (-89 + A * -B)$	$BA + 9876 - 5 - 43 * -2 + 1$
9A37	17035	$1 + 2 + 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 - 8 + 9 + A + B$	$-BA + 9876 + 54 * 3 * 2 - 1$
9A38	17036	$-1 + 234 - (5 + 6) * (-78 - 9AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - 54 * 3 * -2 * 1$
9A39	17037	$12 - 3 - 4 + 5 * (67 - 89) * -AB$	$BA + 9876 + 54 + 32 - 1$
9A3A	17038	$1 + 234 + (-5 - 6) * (-78 - 9AB)$	$BA + 9876 + 54 + 32 * 1$
9A3B	17039	$(-1 + 2 ^{\wedge} (3 + 4)) * (5 - (6 + (-7 - 8) * 9)) + A + B$	$BA - (-9876 - 54) - (-32 - 1)$
9A40	17040	$1 * (2 + 3) * 4 * (-5 - 6 + 7 - 8 * (-9A + B))$	$BA * (9 - 87 + 6 + 54) * (3 + 2) * -1$
9A41	17041	$-1 + 2345 + (-67 + 89A) * B$	$B - (-A + 987) + 6 * 5 * 432 - 1$
9A42	17042	$(-1 / -2 + 3 / 4) * -5 * -6 * 7 - 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - (-A + 987) - 6 * -5 * 432 * 1$
9A43	17043	$1 + 2345 + (-67 + 89A) * B$	$-B - (A - 9876) - 5 * (-43 - 2 - 1)$
9A44	17044	$1 * 2 + (3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 + 6 * 7 * 8 + 9 - A * B$	$BA - (-9876 - 5) - (43 * -2 - 1)$
9A45	17045	$1 + 2 * 345 * 6 * 78 * (-9 + AB)$	$-BA + 9876 - (54 - 321)$
9A46	17046	$-1 * (23 - (4 + 5)) * (678 - 9) * (A - B)$	$-B + A + 9876 + 5 * 43 - 2 * 1$
9A47	17047	$-1 - 2 + 3456 - 78 * (9 - AB)$	$-BA - (98 + 76 * -54 * 3 - 21)$
9A48	17048	$-1 - 2345 * -6 + 7 * 8 * -9A + B$	$-B + A + 9876 - 5 * -43 * (2 - 1)$
9A49	17049	$1 - 2 + 3456 + 78 * (-9 + AB)$	$-B + A * (-98 - 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 * -321)$
9A4A	17050	$1 * 2 + 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 8 + 9 + A + B$	$B * -A * (9 + 8 - (-76 + 5 - 43 - 2)) * -1$
9A4B	17051	$(-1 / (-2 * -3) + 4 + 5 * 6) * -7 * -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - (A - 9876 + 54 * (-3 - 2 + 1))$
9A50	17052	$12 * (34 - 56 - (-789 - AB))$	$B - A - (987 + 6 * 5 * (-432 - 1))$
9A51	17053	$1 - 2 * (-3 + (-4 * 5 - 6 * 7) * 8) - 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9876 + 5 - 4 * (-3 - 21)$
9A52	17054	$-1 + (-2 * 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * -7 * (-6 - 5 * (-4 * 3 + 2)) * 1$
9A53	17055	$(1 + 2 + 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-B + A * 987 + 6 - 5 * -432 * 1$
9A54	17056	$-12 + 34 + 5 * (67 - 89) * -AB$	$BA + 9876 - 5 * -4 * (3 + 2 + 1)$
9A55	17057	$1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 + 6) + (-7 - 8) * 9) + A * B$	$BA + 9876 + 5 * 4 * 3 * 2 + 1$
9A56	17058	$-1 - 2 + 34 * -56 * -7 + 8 - 9AB$	$B + A + 9 * (-8 * 7 + 6 * 5 / 4 + 3 * 2) ^{\wedge} 1$
9A57	17059	$1 * 2 * (3 + (4 * 5 + 6 * 7) * 8 + 9) - (A + B)$	$-B + A + 9876 + 5 * (43 + 2) + 1$
9A58	17060	$12 + 3 - 456 - (-7 - 8) * 9 * AB$	$-B + A * 9 - 8 - 7 * (6 - 54 * 32 - 1)$
9A59	17061	$-123 + 4 + (-56 - 7) * (-89 - AB)$	$-B * (-A98 - (-7 - 6) + 5 - (4 * 3 + 2 - 1))$
9A5A	17062	$-12 + 3 * 4 * (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 9AB)$	$-B + A987 + (-65 + 4) * (-3 + 21)$
9A5B	17063	$-1 + 23 * (-456 - (7 - (89A + B)))$	$-B + A + 9876 + 5 * (43 - (-2 - 1))$
9A60	17064	$1 * 23 * (-4 - 567 - (-8 - 9AB))$	$BA + 9876 - 54 * (-3 - (-2 + 1))$
9A61	17065	$(-1 - 2 * (3 / 4 + 5 * 6 + 7)) * -8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$-B * -A + 9 / ((-8 + 7) / (-6 * (5 ^{\wedge} 4 + 3))) * 2 - 1$
9A62	17066	$-12 * (34 - (-56 - 789)) * (A - B)$	$BA + 9876 + 5 * (43 - 21)$
9A63	17067	$(-1 - 2 * 3 + 4 * 5 - (6 + 7)) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6 + 5 * 4 * 3 - 2) ^{\wedge} 1$
9A64	17068	$-1 + 234 * 5 - 6 - 7 * 89 * (-A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4) * 3 ^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$
9A65	17069	$12 + 3 - (-4 + 567 + 8 + 9) * (-A - B)$	$-BA - 9 + (8 - 76) * -5 * (4 + 32 * 1)$
9A66	17070	$1 * 2 * (3 + (4 * 5 + 6 * 7) * 8) + 9 + A - B$	$B + A * (-98 + 765) + 4321$
9A67	17071	$-1 - 23 - 4 * -56 * 7 + 89AB$	$B + A * (9 + 8 + 7 * 6) / (5 + 4 * 3) ^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$
9A68	17072	$1 * 2 + 34 + 5 * (-67 + 89) * AB$	$B * (A + 9 + 8 - 7 + 65) * -4 * (-3 - 2 + 1)$
9A69	17073	$1 + 2 + 34 + 5 * (-67 + 89) * AB$	$B + A + 9876 + 5 * 43 - (-2 - 1)$
9A6A	17074	$1 * -2 + 3 * -4 * (-5 - 6 - (-7 - 8 + 9AB))$	$-BA - 9 - (-8 + 76 - 543) * 21$
9A6B	17075	$1 + (-2 ^{\wedge} -3 + 4 + 5 * 6) * -7 * -8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA9 + 8765 - 4 + 321$
9A70	17076	$1 * -2 * (34 + 5 - 678 * 9 - (-A - B))$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 * -7 * (6 * 5 + 4)) * 3 ^{\wedge} 2 ^{\wedge} 1$
9A71	17077	$(1 + 2 + 3) ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 ^{\wedge} 6 - (-7 - 8) * 9 + A + B$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 * -7 * (-6 * 5 + 4)) / 3 ^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$
9A72	17078	$1 * -2 * (3 + 4 * 5 + 6 * (-7 - 8) * -9AB)$	$-B - A + (9 + 8 * 7) * (6 + 5) + 4 ^{\wedge} (3 * 2 + 1)$
9A73	17079	$1 * 2 * (3 + (4 * 5 + 6 * 7) * 8 + 9) + A - B$	$BA + 9876 - (5 - 4 * (32 - 1))$
9A74	17080	$12 * (34 + 56 + 789 - A + B)$	$B + A + 9 + (-8 * -7 * 6 + 5) * ((4 + 3) ^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
9A75	17081	$12345 + 6 * (-7 - 89A + B)$	$B + A + 9876 + 5 * (43 + 2) + 1$
9A76	17082	$-12 - 3 + 4 * -56 * -7 + 89AB$	$B + A + 9 * (8 - 7 + 6 + 5 * 4) * 3 - 2 - 1$
9A77	17083	$1 ^{\wedge} 2 * 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA9 + 8765 + 4 + 321$
9A78	17084	$1 + 2 + 3 ^{\wedge} 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9876 - 5 - 4 * -32 + 1$
9A79	17085	$(-1 - 2 * (3 ^{\wedge} 4 + 5 * 6 + 7)) * -8 * 9 + A + B$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6 + 5 * 4 * 3) ^{\wedge} (2 - 1)$
9A7A	17086	$1 - 2 * ((-3 - 4 * 5 - 6 * 7) * 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A - 9 * (-8 + 7 - (6 + 5 * 4)) * 3 + 2 - 1$
9A7B	17087	$-1 * -2 ^{\wedge} 3 * -4 * (-5 * 6 - 7 * 8 * 9) + A - B$	$-BA + 98 * (76 - 5) + 4321$
9A80	17088	$-12 - (-3 + 4 * -56 * 7 - 89AB)$	$-B - (-A - 9876 + 5) - 4 * -3 * 21$
9A81	17089	$1 ^{\wedge} 2 + (3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 - 6 * (-7 * 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 + 5 * -4 + 321$
9A82	17090	$-1 + 23 * 456 - 7 - (89 + AB)$	$B - A - (-9876 + 5 - 4 * -3 * -21)$
9A83	17091	$-1 * 23 * (-456 + 7 - (8 - 9 + A - B))$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * 7 + (6 + 5 * 4) ^{\wedge} 3 - 2 * 1$
9A84	17092	$1 * 2 + (3 + 4) ^{\wedge} 5 - 6 * (-7 * 8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * 7 + (6 + 5 * 4) ^{\wedge} 3 - 2 + 1$
9A85	17093	$-1 - 2 * (-3 - (4 * 5 + 6 * 7)) * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + 9876 + 54 * (3 + 2) * 1$
9A86	17094	$-12 * (-3 + 4 + 56 - 7 - 89A - B)$	$B - A * 9 + 8 * 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 * 3 * -21$
9A87	17095	$12 - 34 * -5 * 67 + 89A + B$	$BA - 9 * 8 + (76 - 543) * -21$
9A88	17096	$-1234 - 56 - 78 * (9 + A) * -B$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * 7 + (6 + 5 * 4) ^{\wedge} 3 + 2 + 1$
9A89	17097	$-1 + 2 - (3 - 4 * 56 * 7 - 89AB)$	$BA + 9876 + 5 - 4 * (-32 - 1)$
9A8A	17098	$-1 + (-2 - 3) * (-4 + (-5 - 6 * 7) * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 * (8 - 7 * 6) + 5) / (4 * 3 - 2 * 1)$
9A8B	17099	$-1 - 2 + 3 + 4 * 56 * 7 + 89AB$	$B + A + (-9 * (8 - 7 * 6) + 5) / (4 * 3 - 2) + 1$
9A90	17100	$123 * -4 * (56 - 7 - (89 - A - B))$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 - (4 - 321)$
9A91	17101	$-1 - 23 * -456 - 78 - 9 - AB$	$B + A + 9 * 8 * 7 * (6 * 5 + 4 - 3 - 2) ^{\wedge} 1$
9A92	17102	$1 + (-2 - 3) * (-4 + (-5 - 6 * 7) * 8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$-BA - 98 + 765 * 4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$
9A93	17103	$-1 + 2 + 3 - (-4 * -56 * -7 - 89AB)$	$BA + 9876 + 54 * 3 - 21$
9A94	17104	$(-1 - 2 * (-3 - 4 * 5 - 6 * 7)) * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 - (8 + 7 * (6 + 5) ^{\wedge} 4)) / (-3 * 2) - 1$
9A95	17105	$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 * -56 * -7 + 89AB$	$B + A + (9 + 8 * 7 * (6 + 5) ^{\wedge} 4) / (3 + 2 + 1)$
9A96	17106	$-1 - (-234 - 567 * (8 - 9)) * (-A - B)$	$-B - A + 9876 + (5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$
9A97	17107	$1 - 2 + (-3 + (-4 - 5 * 6) * -7 * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - 9 * (8 + 7 - 6 * -5 * -4 * 3 + 2) + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9A98	17108	$(-1-2)^*(-3^*(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5+4+321$
9A99	17109	$1+2+34^*-5^*-67+8+9A^*B$	$-B+A^*(987+6)+5^*-432^*-1$
9A9A	17110	$12-3+4^*-56^*-7+89AB$	$-BA-(-9876-5+4-321)$
9A9B	17111	$-1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5+6^*7))^*8+9+A-B$	$-BA9+8-7^*6^*(5-(-4+321))$
9AA0	17112	$-1+23^*456-78-9A-B$	$-BA-9+8+76^*54^*3-21$
9AA1	17113	$12-3-(4^*(-56+7))^*8^*9+A^*-B$	$B+A+9^*(-8^*(-7+6)+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2-1$
9AA2	17114	$1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(6^*-7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*(8^{\wedge}(7-6)+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
9AA3	17115	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(6^*-7+8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+6^*-54^*-3^*(2+1))$
9AA4	17116	$1^*-23+4567-8^*-9^*AB$	$B^*-A98^*(7+6-5-(4+3^*2-1))$
9AA5	17117	$1-(23-4567)-8^*9^*-AB$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*-7^*(-6^*-5-4^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
9AA6	17118	$(-1+2)^*3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8^*9-(A+B)$	$-BA+9876-(-5-4-321)$
9AA7	17119	$-1^*(234-5)^*(-67-(89-AB))$	$-B^*-A-9^*(-8-7)^*(6-5^*-4^*3^*2)-1$
9AA8	17120	$1-23^*(-456+7)-(-89+AB)$	$-B-(-A987+6)+543^*2^*1$
9AA9	17121	$1-23^*-456-78+9-AB$	$-B-(-A987+6)-543^*2+1$
9AAA	17122	$123-4^*-567+89^*AB$	$-BA-9-8-76^*54^*-3+2-1$
9AAB	17123	$(-1-2^*3^4)^*-5^*(6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8-7+(6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
9AB0	17124	$-1-234^*(-56+7)-(-8-9)^*-A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
9AB1	17125	$-1+2^*3-4-(5+6+7+8)^*-9AB$	$BA+9876+54^*3-2-1$
9AB2	17126	$1^*23-4^*-56^*7+89AB$	$BA+9876-54^*-3+2^*-1$
9AB3	17127	$1^*(2-345-678-9A)^*-B$	$BA+9876+54^*3-2+1$
9AB4	17128	$-1-2+3+4+(5+6-7+8)^*9AB$	$BA+9876-54^*3^*(-2+1)$
9AB5	17129	$1^*-2^*3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876+5^*-4)+321$
9AB6	17130	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$-BA9^*(-8+76-54-3-21)$
9AB7	17131	$-1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$B-(A9+8^*-7^*-65^*-4)-(-3+2)^*1$
9AB8	17132	$-12-(-3-4567-8^*9^*AB)$	$-BA+987+6-543^*2^*-1$
9AB9	17133	$1^{\wedge}2^*(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$B-A-987+6^*5^*(432-1)$
9ABA	17134	$-1-23^*-456-78-9A+B$	$B-A9-(-8^*-7^*65^*-4-(3+2-1))$
9ABB	17135	$-1-234-(-5+67)^*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987+6^*5^*-43-2-1$
9B00	17136	$12-3^*(-4-5)^*(67-8)^*9-AB$	$-BA+9-8+76^*54^*3-2-1$
9B01	17137	$-1-2-3+4567-8^*9^*-AB$	$-B+A987-(6-543)^*-2-1$
9B02	17138	$-1^*-2^*(34-56-(7+8))^*(-9-A)^*B$	$-B^*(-A98-7-(6-5-4-3))-(-2-1)$
9B03	17139	$1^{\wedge}2+3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6^*5^*43+2-1$
9B04	17140	$-1^*-2^*(3+4567-8^*(-9A+B))$	$B-A-98-(76^*54^*-3+21)$
9B05	17141	$-1+2-3+4567-8^*-9^*AB$	$BA+9876-5^*(-4-(32-1))$
9B06	17142	$-12-3^*(-456+7)+89AB$	$B-(-A987-(-6-543^*2^*1))$
9B07	17143	$-1^*-2^{\wedge}3-(-4-5^6)^*-7^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6-543^*-2-1)$
9B08	17144	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4-5^6)^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7/6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1$
9B09	17145	$1+(-2+3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-A9+8-(-76^*-54^*-3+2+1)$
9B0A	17146	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5+6-7)^*(8+9)-A^*B$	$-BA-9-(8+76^*54^*-3)+21$
9B0B	17147	$-1+2+3+4567+8^*9^*AB$	$B+A-9^*(8+7-6^*-5^*-4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
9B10	17148	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(8+7-6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}1$
9B11	17149	$1-(-2-3-4567)-8^*9^*-AB$	$B^*(-A98-(-7+6)+5-(4+3+2))^*-1$
9B12	17150	$-1+2-(345+678+9A)^*-B$	$-B-A9-(-8-76^*-54^*-3-2^*1)$
9B13	17151	$1-23^*(-456+7)-89-A^*-B$	$BA+9876-5^*(-4-32-1)$
9B14	17152	$1-2^*3^*-45^*-6^*(7-8)^*9-A-B$	$B-(A9+8^*-7^*-65^*-4)-(3-21)$
9B15	17153	$1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA-(-9876-54^*3)+21$
9B16	17154	$12-3+4567-8^*-9^*AB$	$B+A987+6-543^*2^*1$
9B17	17155	$-12+3-4^*-567+89A^*B$	$B+A987+6+543^*-2+1$
9B18	17156	$-1^*(2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)^*(6+(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8^*7^*(6^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3-2)-1$
9B19	17157	$-1+2-3^*(-456+7)+89AB$	$B+A9-8-76^*54^*-3+2+1$
9B1A	17158	$-1-2^*-3^*-4^*(-5-6)^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B-A^*-987-65^*(-4-32+1)$
9B1B	17159	$(-1+2/3+(-4-5^6)^*7)^*-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*-7^*(-6^*-5-4^{\wedge}3)+2^*1$
9B20	17160	$-1^*2^*3^*4^*(5-67+8-9+A)^*B$	$B^*A^*(-9+8+76+54+3)^*(2-1)$
9B21	17161	$1-2^*3+4^*567+89A^*B$	$-BA+9876-5^*-43^*2-1$
9B22	17162	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3+(-4+5^6)^*-7^*-8^*-9+A-B$	$-BA-(-9876-5^*-43^*2^*-1)$
9B23	17163	$1^{\wedge}2-(-3+(-4-5^6)^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+6^*5^*43-21)$
9B24	17164	$-1+2-3-4^*-567+89A^*B$	$-B-(-A+98)-76^*54^*-3-(-2+1)$
9B25	17165	$12345-6^*(-7+89A-B)$	$B+A987-(-6-(-54-3))^*21$
9B26	17166	$1^*2-(-3+(-4-5^6)^*7^*8)^*9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+9876-54+321$
9B27	17167	$1-2^*-3^*-45^*-6-(-7-89AB)$	$-BA9+8^*(765+43^*21)$
9B28	17168	$1-2+3+4^*567-89A^*-B$	$B+A9^*(87-(6-54+3+21))$
9B29	17169	$-1+23+4567-8^*9^*-AB$	$B+A-9^*(8+7-6^*-5^*-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1$
9B2A	17170	$-12-3^*-456+7+89AB$	$B+A+(9-8^*-7^*6+5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
9B2B	17171	$-1^*(2+345+678+9A)^*-B$	$-B^*(-A-987-(65-4+3)^*2^*-1)$
9B30	17172	$1-23^*-456-7^*8-9A+B$	$B-A9^*-8-7^*6^*-54^*-3^*-2+1$
9B31	17173	$-1234-(5-6+78^*(9A)^*-B)$	$-BA+9876+54+321$
9B32	17174	$(-1-(-2/-3-(-4-5^6)^*7)^*-8)^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5^*-4^*-3^*21$
9B33	17175	$1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^*8+9+A+B$	$B-A+9876+5^*(43+21)$
9B34	17176	$1234+5^*-6^*7^*-8^*-9^*(A-B)$	$B+A-9^*(8+(-7-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+2-1$
9B35	17177	$-1-(2^{\wedge}3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6+7)^*(8+9))+A-B$	$-B+A+9876-54^*3^*-2^*1$
9B36	17178	$1^*2345+6+(-78-9)^*-AB$	$B-A+9876-54^*3^*-2-1$
9B37	17179	$1-(2^{\wedge}3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6+7)^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B-A9-8+76^*-54^*-3+21$
9B38	17180	$(-1+2^*3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8-76^*-54^*3+21$
9B39	17181	$1-(-2-3+(-4-5^6)^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9^*8-7+6+5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
9B3A	17182	$1-23^*-456+7^*8-(-9-A)^*-B$	$-B^*(-A98-(7-65)-43-21)$
9B3B	17183	$12-(-3+4^*-567)-89A^*-B$	$-BA+9^*(-8+7+65+4-3)^*21$
9B40	17184	$12-3^*-456-(7-89AB)$	$B+A987-6+5^*-4^*-3^*-21$
9B41	17185	$-1+2-3^*-456-(-7-89AB)$	$-B-(A-9^*(8+765))+4321$
9B42	17186	$12-3^*45^*(6+7+8-9A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-54-321)$
9B43	17187	$1+2-3^*-456+7+89AB$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*(7^*(-6+5^*4+3)^*2+1)$
9B44	17188	$-1-(-2^*-3-(-4-5^6)^*-7^*-8)^*-9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-(-54+321))$
9B45	17189	$-1+23^*456-(7+8)-(9A+B)$	$-B+A+9^*(8+7-(-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+2^{\wedge}1$
9B46	17190	$1+(-2^*-3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5^*43-2-1$
9B47	17191	$(-1/-2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7/(-8^*9))+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8^*7+6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
9B48	17192	$-1+23+4^*567+89A^*B$	$BA+9876-5^*-43-(-2+1)$
9B49	17193	$(-1+2+3+(-4-5^6)^*-7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$-B^*(A98+7)^*(-65-(-43-21))$
9B4A	17194	$1+23^*456+7-(8+9+AB)$	$BA+98^*7^*(-6-5+4+3+21)$
9B4B	17195	$-1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B-A9+8+76^*54^*3+21$
9B50	17196	$-1-23-4+(56+7)^*(89+AB)$	$B+A987+6+5^*-4^*3^*21$
9B51	17197	$1-2+3^*(456+7)+89AB$	$-B+A987+6^*5^*(-43+2)-1$
9B52	17198	$1^*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6^*5^*(-43-2^*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
9B53	17199	$-1+2-3*(-456-7)+89AB$	$B+A+9876-54*-3*-2*-1$
9B54	17200	$-1*-2*-34*5*(-6+78-9A-B)$	$B-(-A-9876)-(54*-3*2-1)$
9B55	17201	$(-1-(2^3+4)*5)*-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A*987-(-65-43)*21$
9B56	17202	$-1*(2-34-(5+6)-78)*(-9+AB)$	$BA+9876-5*(-43-2)+1$
9B57	17203	$(1+(2^3-4)^5-(6+7))* (8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8*-7+6)*(-5-4^3)/2+1$
9B58	17204	$-1-2*345+678*(9A)+B$	$B*(A98-7-(6-(-5+43-21)))$
9B59	17205	$123+4-5*(67-89)*AB$	$B+A-9*8*(7+6+(-5-4)^3)/(2+1)$
9B5A	17206	$-12*(34+56+78-9AB)$	$-B-A+9*-8+(7+6+5^4)*3^2(2+1)$
9B5B	17207	$-12+34*56*7-(89A-B)$	$B-A-9*(-8-765)+4321$
9B60	17208	$12-345-6+(-7-8)*9*-AB$	$B+A-(-9876+54)+321$
9B61	17209	$(-1-(-2-3^4(4+5)+6)*7)/8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+(9+(8-7)^6)*(-5-(-4*3)^(2+1))$
9B62	17210	$(-1-2-3^4(4+5)+6)*-7/8-9+A-B$	$-B*-A-9*(-8-7*6)*(5+4^3/2+1)$
9B63	17211	$-1-23*-456-7-8-9A+B$	$B+A+9*(8+7-(-6-5^4)*3+2^1)$
9B64	17212	$12+3*(456+7)+89AB$	$B-A*9+8+76*54*3+2+1$
9B65	17213	$12345+6*(-789-AB)$	$B+A+9*8*7*(6*5+4+3^2-2)^1$
9B66	17214	$1*-2*(3-4-(5678+9*-A*B))$	$B+A+9-8*(7+6-(5+4)^3)*(2+1)$
9B67	17215	$1+(-2+3^4)*(-5*-6*7+8)-9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+(9-(8-7-6)^5)*(4+3/2)-1$
9B68	17216	$(-1+(-2+3^4(4+5)+6)*7)/8-9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5*43+21$
9B69	17217	$1-2+(3+4)^5-6*(7-8*9)+A+B$	$-B-A-(9+8)+76*54*3-21$
9B6A	17218	$(-1+2+3^4)*-5*-6*7+8-9A-B$	$BA9-8*(7+6-54)*32+1$
9B6B	17219	$(-1+2+3^4)*-5*-6*-7*(8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6*5*(-43+2)-1$
9B70	17220	$-12*(3-45+67-89A+B)$	$-B-A+9*8*765*(-4+3)*2*-1$
9B71	17221	$-12+3456-7-8*-9AB$	$-B-A+9876-5-4+321$
9B72	17222	$1+2+34*-5*-67-8+9AB$	$B+A+9-8*-7*((-6*-5+4)/3^2-2+1)$
9B73	17223	$1234-5-67+89AB$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*6*(-5+4^3+2)^1$
9B74	17224	$(-1-2*-3*-4*(5+6))* (7-8*9)+A-B$	$B+A-((-9+8*7)*-6*(-5+4^3+2)-1)$
9B75	17225	$-1+2*(3+4-567+8-9A)*-B$	$-B*-A-9*(-8-(7-(6-5^4)))^3*(2+1)$
9B76	17226	$1*-23*(4+5+6-78+9A)*B$	$-B-A-9+8+7*65*(4+3+21)$
9B77	17227	$123+4-(5+67)*(-8*9-AB)$	$B-A9*-87+65*43-2*-1$
9B78	17228	$-1234+56+78*(9A)*B$	$-BA+9876+54*3*(2+1)$
9B79	17229	$-1-23*-456-78+9-A-B$	$-B-A+9876-5+4+321$
9B7A	17230	$1+2*3*456+789A+B$	$-B+A+9876+5*-4+321$
9B7B	17231	$-1-23*-456-(78+9)-(-A+B)$	$B-A+9876+5-4+321$
9B80	17232	$-1-2+3456-7-8*-9AB$	$B-A+9876-5*4+321$
9B81	17233	$1234+5-(67-89AB)$	$B-A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^3+2)+1$
9B82	17234	$-12*(-345-6*-78-9A*B)$	$BA9-76*(5+4+3+21)$
9B83	17235	$-12+3456+7+8*9AB$	$BA9-(-8765-432+1)$
9B84	17236	$-1+2+3456-7+8*9AB$	$BA9+8765+432*1$
9B85	17237	$-1*(2+(-3-4^5+6+7))*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$BA9-(-8765-432-1)$
9B86	17238	$1+2+3456-(7+8*-9AB)$	$B+A-9*(-8*(-7-6*(-5-4/3^2-2)))-1$
9B87	17239	$1+2+(3+4)^5+(-6+7*8)*9-(A+B)$	$-B-A+9876+5+4+321$
9B88	17240	$(-1+2^3)*-4*(-5-6)*7*8-9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*7-(-6+5^4)*3)+2^1$
9B89	17241	$1*(-23-45-6+7*-89)*(-A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9876+5+4-321)$
9B8A	17242	$-1-2*345*-6-(7-8*9AB)$	$-B-A-9*((-8+7)*-6*-5*4^3+2)+1$
9B8B	17243	$1-(2+3^4*(-56-7*-8-9AB))$	$B-(-A-9876-5-4+321)$
9B90	17244	$1234-56-7+89AB$	$-B*-A-(-9*-8*-7*(-6*5+4^3)+2^1)$
9B91	17245	$(-1/-2*-3+(-4-5*6)*7)*-8*9-(A-B)$	$-B*-A+9*8*7*(6*5+4)^(3-2)-1$
9B92	17246	$-1-(2-3456)-(-7+8*-9AB)$	$BA9-7+65*(-4-32-1)$
9B93	17247	$(-1-2-(-3^4(4+5)+6)*7)/8+9+A+B$	$B+A-9*(8-7*6+5)*(4^3+2)^1$
9B94	17248	$-1*(-23+45-6*7)*(8+9)*B$	$-B*(-A-9*(-87-65)-(-4+32))^*-1$
9B95	17249	$12+3456-7+8*9AB$	$-B-A98-7*-6*-54*(-3*2-1)$
9B96	17250	$-1-(-2-3456)+7+8*9AB$	$-B+A+9876*(5-4)+321$
9B97	17251	$-1*(-2-3456-(7+8*9AB))$	$-B-(-A-9876-5)-(-4-321)$
9B98	17252	$1+2+3456+7+8*9AB$	$B+A+9876+5*-4+321$
9B99	17253	$-1+(-2^3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-A-(-9876-5+4-321)$
9B9A	17254	$-1-23*-456-7+8*9*(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8+(7-6*(5*4+3))^2*1$
9B9B	17255	$1+(-2^3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA+98*(7+65)+4321$
9BA0	17256	$1^2*(3+4)^5+(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+54*(-3-2)*-1$
9BA1	17257	$1^2+(3+4)^5+(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$B-A9-8*(765+4-3)*-2-1$
9BA2	17258	$1234-56+7+89AB$	$B+A+(9+(-8+7+6)^5)*(4+3/-2*-1)$
9BA3	17259	$1+2+(3+4)^5+(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-5-4)+321$
9BA4	17260	$1234-5+6*-7+89AB$	$-BA+9876-5+432-1$
9BA5	17261	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5-(6+7*8))*9+A-B$	$B-A+9876+5+4+321$
9BA6	17262	$-12*(3-4)*(-5-(6-789-AB))$	$-BA-(-9876+5-432-1)$
9BA7	17263	$12+3456+7+8*9AB$	$B+A-(-9876+5+4-321)$
9BA8	17264	$1^2*3^4-4*5*6^7-8-9-(A-B)$	$B-A*98-7+6*5*-432*-1$
9BA9	17265	$(-1/-2*-3+(-4-5*6)*7)*-8*9+A+B$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^5/4+3^2+1)$
9BAA	17266	$-12+3*-4*-5*6*(-78+9+AB)$	$B+A-9*(-8*7-6*-5*(-4^3+2))+1$
9BAB	17267	$-1+(-2^3+4^5-(6-7))*(8+9)-(-A+B)$	$BA98+7*(-654+321)$
9BB0	17268	$-12-34-56-78*-9*(A+B)$	$-B-A+9*(-8+7+6*5*4^3+2)^1$
9BB1	17269	$1+(-2^3+4^5-(6-7))*(8+9)-(-A+B)$	$B+A+9^4(-8+7)*6^5+4^4(3^2+1)$
9BB2	17270	$1234+5-6*7+89AB$	$-BA+9876+5-(-432+1)$
9BB3	17271	$123*(4+56-7-(-8-9)+A+B)$	$-BA+9876+5-432*-1$
9BB4	17272	$-1*(-2-34*-56*-7-(-8+9A)*-B)$	$-BA+9876+5+432+1$
9BB5	17273	$1+23*456-(78-9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A+9876+5-4+321$
9BB6	17274	$1-(2^3+4^5/(6-7))*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A+9*(-8+7+6*5*4^3-2)^1$
9BB7	17275	$-1+(-2^3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^3+2)+1$
9BB8	17276	$-123-(-45-6)-78*-9*(A+B)$	$B+A+((-9-8)*7*6+5)*-4*-3*2-1$
9BB9	17277	$1+(-2^3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A*98+7*6*54*3*2*-1$
9BBA	17278	$-1*2*(34-5-678*9)*(A-B)$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(-6+5^4-3)*2^1-1$
9BBB	17279	$-1-23*(-4+567-(8+9AB))$	$BA+9876-(5+4)*-32+1$
A000	17280	$-1*23*(-456+7-(-89-A*-B))$	$BA-9*-8+7*(6-54*-32*1)$
A001	17281	$1+23*-4*(-5+6)+78*-9*(A-B)$	$B+A*(-987+6*(54+321))$
A002	17282	$1*2-((-3-4)^5-6*(7+8*9))+A-B$	$-B+A987-65*(-4-3+21)$
A003	17283	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5-(6+7*8))*9+A+B$	$-B-(-A987+654+321)$
A004	17284	$1234+5*-6+7+89AB$	$-B-(-A-9876)-(-5*43*-2-1)$
A005	17285	$-1-23*-456-(-78+9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8-7*(6-5^4))*(3+2-1)$
A006	17286	$1*2*(345-6*78)*(-9A-B)$	$-B-A+9*(8-7+6*5*4^3+2)^1$
A007	17287	$1-23*-456-(-78-(-9-AB))$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^5/4+3^2)+1$
A008	17288	$(-1*-2*-3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-54*(-3+21)$
A009	17289	$-1+2345-6-(-789A+B)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^3)-(-2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A00A	17290	$-1 * (-2+3+45+67) * (-8 - (-9+AB))$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^{\wedge}3)-2*1$
A00B	17291	$1 - (-2345+6) - (-789A+B)$	$-BA-9 - (-87-6-5)*-43*(2-1)$
A010	17292	$1*(234-56)*(7*-8-(9-AB))$	$B*(A98-7-(6+5-(-4+32*1)))$
A011	17293	$1+2*(345+6-(7+89A))*-B$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^{\wedge}3)+2-1$
A012	17294	$1-(2^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5/(6-7))*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A-(-9876-54-321)$
A013	17295	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8*9-(A+B)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6*-5*-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1$
A014	17296	$-1+23*456+78-9A-B$	$BA9+8+7*(65-4*3)*-21$
A015	17297	$((1^{\wedge}2+3)^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6+7))/-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+9*8*(7-6*5/4*3)^{\wedge}2/1$
A016	17298	$1-23*-456+78-9A-B$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8-7)*6*5*4^{\wedge}3-2-1$
A017	17299	$1234+5-6-(7-89AB)$	$B+A*98-7*6*5*4*3*-2*1$
A018	17300	$-1-23*-456-7+89-AB$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8-7)*6*5*4^{\wedge}3-2+1$
A019	17301	$1234-5+6-7+89AB$	$B+A+9*(8+7+65-4*-321)$
A01A	17302	$1*2345-(-6-789A+B)$	$B+A+9^{\wedge}(8-7)*6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2-1$
A01B	17303	$1+2345-(-6-789A)-B$	$B*(A+98-765-432)*-1$
A020	17304	$-12*-3*-4*(5-(6-7+8))-(-9-A*-B)$	$-B-A-9*(87-65+43)*-21$
A021	17305	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-654-321$
A022	17306	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA-9-8*7*65*-4-3*21$
A023	17307	$-1-23*-456-(7-8*(9-A))-B$	$B+A-9-(8+76*-5*4*3-21)$
A024	17308	$-1-2*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6+7*8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*(7+(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3))*(2+1))$
A025	17309	$1-2*-3456-7*8*(9*-A-B)$	$BA98+765*(4-(3-2))*-1$
A026	17310	$(1+2*3)^{\wedge}(4-5+6)+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8+7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}1$
A027	17311	$-1+2345-(-6-789A-B)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4+3^{\wedge}2+1$
A028	17312	$1*2345-6+789A+B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6*-5*-4^{\wedge}3)+2/1$
A029	17313	$1234+5-(6-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)*(-6/5+(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
A02A	17314	$123+456+7+8*9*-AB$	$-B+A-(-9876-54-321)$
A02B	17315	$1234-5+6+7+89AB$	$BA-9-8+76*(-5*3-(-2-1))$
A030	17316	$1+23*456-(-7-89+AB)$	$B-A+9876+54+321$
A031	17317	$1-2+3*45*(6+7)+89AB$	$B+A-9*-8*(7*-6+5)*(4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
A032	17318	$-1+23*456+7-(-8+9+A+B)$	$B+A+9*8*(7-6*5/4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
A033	17319	$-1-23*(-456-7)+8*-9-AB$	$-B+A*(-9+8)*(76+5-4*321)$
A034	17320	$1-23*-456+78-9A+B$	$BA+9876-54*3*-2*1$
A035	17321	$1+23*(456+7)+8*-9-AB$	$BA+9876-54*3*-2+1$
A036	17322	$1-23*-456-78+9*A-B$	$B+A+(9*-8+7-6^{\wedge}5/-4*3)*(2+1)$
A037	17323	$-1+2345+6+789A+B$	$-B-A-9*(8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4+3)+2-1$
A038	17324	$-12-3-45+6-78*9*(-A-B)$	$-BA*(-9+8-(76-(-5-43)-21))$
A039	17325	$1+2345+6+789A+B$	$B*(-A98+7-65+43)*(-2+1)$
A03A	17326	$12+34*-5*-6-7-8*-9*(A+B)$	$B+A+9-8*(7+(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3))*(2+1))$
A03B	17327	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8*9+A+B$	$B-(-A-9-(-8+76*-5*4*-3+21))$
A040	17328	$1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8*9+A+B$	$-B+A9-8*-7*65*4-32*1$
A041	17329	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7*8*9+A+B$	$BA+9876-54+321$
A042	17330	$-1-2*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5+6+7*8)*9)+A+B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3-2)-1$
A043	17331	$1-2+3-(45+6)-78*9*(-A-B)$	$B+A+9*8*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
A044	17332	$-12*(3+45-(6+7)-89A-B)$	$B+A+9*8*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2^{\wedge}1)$
A045	17333	$(-1-2)*-3*(-4-5*-6*7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
A046	17334	$-1*-23*(4-5)*6*(7+8+9-AB)$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)-3*2^{\wedge}1$
A047	17335	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8*9+A+B$	$-B-A9*(8+7)+6+543*21$
A048	17336	$1+(-2-(-3+(-4-5*6)*7)*8)*9-(A-B)$	$B-(-A-9876-54)+321$
A049	17337	$1+2+3*456*(7-8-(-9+A)+B)$	$BA98+7+65*(-4-32)*1$
A04A	17338	$-1234-56+(-7-8)*-9A*B$	$B+A987-(65+43*21)$
A04B	17339	$(-1+2+3-4^{\wedge}5)/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}2-2^{\wedge}1)$
A050	17340	$1+(-2-(3-4^{\wedge}5+6)+7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A98+7*(-65+4)*(-32+1)$
A051	17341	$1+2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7*8*9+A+B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)+3-2/1$
A052	17342	$(-1-2)*(-3-4*5*6)*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)+3-(2-1)$
A053	17343	$-1+(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*(-8-9)+A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8)/(7-6)*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
A054	17344	$1234+5*6-(-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(9+8)*(7-6-5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))$
A055	17345	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7)*(-8-9)+A+B$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4+3+2)-1$
A056	17346	$-12*(34+56+7*-8+9)*(-A-B)$	$B+A+9*(87-65+43)*21$
A057	17347	$1-23*-456+7-89-A*-B$	$-B*(-A98-(-7+65))-(-43+2)*1$
A058	17348	$-1-23*-456-78+9A-B$	$-B-A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)+3^{\wedge}2-1$
A059	17349	$1*-2+(-3+(-4+5*-6)*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)/2-1$
A05A	17350	$1-2+(-3+(-4-5*6)*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*(-7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)/-2*1$
A05B	17351	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3+4-5*-6*7)*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)/2+1$
A060	17352	$1^{\wedge}2+(-3+(-4-5*6)*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)-(2+1)$
A061	17353	$-1*-2+(-3+(-4+5*6)*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876+5*-4*(3+21))$
A062	17354	$1234-(-5-6*7-89AB)$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)-(2-1)$
A063	17355	$-12+3456-7+89*A*B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)/(2-1)$
A064	17356	$-1+23*456+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)+2-1$
A065	17357	$(-1*-2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*-6*7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)+2^{\wedge}1$
A066	17358	$-1-23*-456-(-7-(8+9-A+B))$	$B*(A98-(-7+6-(5*4+3))-2*-1))$
A067	17359	$-1+2345+67*(-8-9)*-A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)*-2^{\wedge}1-1$
A068	17360	$12*-34*(5-(6-78))-(-9+AB))$	$-B-A+(-9*-8+7)*(-6-5)*-4*(3+2)+1$
A069	17361	$(-1*-2*((3-4)^{\wedge}5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9+A-B$	$BA+9-8*-7*65*4-32*1$
A06A	17362	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4+3)-2^{\wedge}1$
A06B	17363	$-1+23*456-78-9+AB$	$-B*-A+9*(8+7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}1$
A070	17364	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3-2-1)$
A071	17365	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5-(-6-7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A9-(8-76*54*3+21)$
A072	17366	$1-23*-456-(7-(8+9)-A-B)$	$-B+A9+8*7*-65*-4+3-(2+1)$
A073	17367	$-12-3-4+(-5+6)*-7*8*9*(-A-B)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4+3)+2+1$
A074	17368	$1-2+3456-7-89*A*B$	$-B-A-9*-8*-7*-6*(-5/-4*3+2)+1$
A075	17369	$-12+3456+7+89*A*B$	$-B*(A9-876-5-(-4+321))$
A076	17370	$-1+2-(-3456+7)+89*A*B$	$-B+A*98*7+6-(-5432-1)$
A077	17371	$-1+23*(456-7+8)*(-9+A)+B$	$BA98+7-(-65-43)*-21$
A078	17372	$1+2+3456-7+89*-A*-B$	$BA987-(-6-5+4)*-321$
A079	17373	$((1-2)^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}5+6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A9876-5*4+321$
A07A	17374	$1-2+(-3+4^{\wedge}5-6+7)*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4+3-2)+1$
A07B	17375	$-1-2*-3*(4-5)-(6+7*8*-9*(A+B))$	$-B-A+98+76*5*4*3*(-2+1)$
A080	17376	$1234+56-7+89AB$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)-3*2^{\wedge}1$
A081	17377	$1*2+(-3-(-4^{\wedge}5+6)+7)*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$B+A-9*(8+7+6^{\wedge}5/-4)-3-2*1$
A082	17378	$1234-56*(78-9+AB))$	$-B+A987-6*-5*(-4-32-1)$
A083	17379	$1+2-(-3+4)-(-5+6)-78*9*(-A-B)$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6^{\wedge}5/4)-3*(2-1)$
A084	17380	$-1*-2*(-3+4)*(567-8+9-A)*B$	$BA-9-8+76*54*3-21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A085	17381	1234-5-(-67-89AB)	-B-A-(-9876-(-5+432-1))
A086	17382	-12-(-3-4)-(5-6+78*-9*(A+B))	-B-(A-9876)-(5+432*-1)
A087	17383	12+3456-(7-89*A*B)	-B-A-(-9876+5-432)+1
A088	17384	-1*-234*(56+7-8+9-A-B)	BA+9876-5-(4-321)
A089	17385	-1*2+(-3/-4+5)*-6*-7*8*9+A-B	B+A987-6*5+43*-21
A08A	17386	1+2+3456+7+89*-A*-B	-B-A-98*(76-54)-321
A08B	17387	(-1*-2-3/-4*5)*-6*-7*8*9+A-B	B+A-9*(8+7-6^5/4)+3+2^1
A090	17388	1*(2+345)*(6-78-9+AB)	-B+A9-8-76*54*-3-2*1
A091	17389	1*2+(-3/-4+5)*-6*-7*8*9+A-B	B+A-9*(8+7-6^5/4)-3*-2+1
A092	17390	1234+56+7+89AB	-B+A9-8-76*54*3*(-2+1)
A093	17391	1234+56+7+89AB	-B-A+9876+5+432-1
A094	17392	(-1-2+3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)-(A-B)	BA+9876-5+4+321
A095	17393	1-(-2+3+4^5/(6-7))*(8+9)-(A-B)	-B-(A-9876-5-432-1)
A096	17394	1-2+(-3+4^5-6+7)*(8+9)+A+B	BA+9876+5-(4-321)
A097	17395	-1-2+34-5*6+78*9*(A+B)	-B+A+98+76*54*-3*(-2+1)
A098	17396	(-1-2+(-3/-4+5)*-6*-7*8)*9+A-B	B-A+98-76*-54*3*-2+1
A099	17397	12+3456+7+89*A*B	-BA9-8-7+(-6+543)*21
A09A	17398	12+3+4-5-6-78*9*(A-B)	-BA+9876-(-543+21)
A09B	17399	-1*2^3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	BA98-76+5*(-432-1)
A0A0	17400	-1*-2*-3*4*5*(-6-7+8-9-AB)	-B-(A-98+76*54*3-21)
A0A1	17401	1+23*456-7*8-9+AB	-B+A+9876-(5-432)-1
A0A2	17402	-12*(3-(456+7*89-AB))	BA+9876+5+4+321
A0A3	17403	1-2-3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	B-A+9876-5+432-1
A0A4	17404	-1/-2*(3-4^5*(-6*7+8)-9)+A-B	BA98-76+5*-432*1
A0A5	17405	1^2-3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	B-A+9876-5+432+1
A0A6	17406	1/(2-3)-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	B+A+9*8*7+6+5^4*3^3(2+1)
A0A7	17407	-1*-2^3*-4^5*(6+7/8-9)+A-B	B+A-9*(8+7-6^5/4-3)-2^1
A0A8	17408	1+23+4*5*(-6-78+9+A)*-B	B+A-9*-8*-7*-6*(-5/-4*3+2)-1
A0A9	17409	1-2+3+4^5/((6-7)/(8-9))+A-B	BA98-(76-5*(-432+1))
A0AA	17410	-1+23*456-7-(-89+A)-B	B+A-9*-8*-7*-6*(-5/-4*3+2)+1
A0AB	17411	1^A-2+3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	-BA98+765*(-4+32+1)
A0B0	17412	1*2+3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	BA98-76*5*(4+3)+2*-1
A0B1	17413	-1-23*-456-(-78-9+A+B)	-B-(-A-9876-5-432-1)
A0B2	17414	(-1-2^3-4*5*6)*(-7-8)*9+A-B	BA98-76*-5*(4+3)*(-2+1)
A0B3	17415	-1-(-2+34-56-78*9*(A+B))	B-A+9876+5+432+1
A0B4	17416	1+2^3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A-B	B+A9876+5+43*-21
A0B5	17417	-1*-2^3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)-(A-B)	B+A+98+76*-54*-3*(2-1)
A0B6	17418	-12-3+45-6+78*9*(A+B)	B+A+9*(8+7+6*5*4^3-2)^1
A0B7	17419	1-23*-456+78-(9+A-B)	-B-A+9*(8+7+6+5^4)*3-2^1
A0B8	17420	(-1-2)*3-4^5/(6-7)*(8+9)+A+B	-BA+9876+543-2-1
A0B9	17421	(-1+(-2-3^4)*-5*6)*7+8-9+A-B	-BA+9876+543+2*-1
A0BA	17422	-1+2+3*(4+5)+6-78*-9*(A+B)	-BA-(-9876-543+2)+1
A0BB	17423	1*2-3+(45+67)*(-8+9+AB)	-BA+9876+543*(2-1)
A100	17424	-1+23*456+7-(-89+A+B)	-BA+9876+543+2-1
A101	17425	1+(2*3)^4+5^6+7*8*9+A-B	B+A-(-9876+5-432-1)
A102	17426	-1-(2+(-3-4)*-5*(6-7*8*9))+A-B	B-(-A987-6)-(-5+43*21)
A103	17427	1*(2+34-5)*(-678+9AB)	-BA9-(8-7+(6-543)*21)
A104	17428	-1*(-2-3^4)*-5*-6*7+8-9+A-B	B+A-98*(76-54)-321
A105	17429	1+(-2-3^4)*-5*6*7+8-9+A-B	B+A+(9+8-7-6)^5+4^4(3^2+1)
A106	17430	12*(3-(-4-5*6-(-7+89A+B)))	B+A+(-9+8+7+6+5)*4^4(3+2)+1
A107	17431	-1+23*456+7*(8+9)-A-B	BA98-7+6*(-54-321)
A108	17432	1+23*456+7+89-(-A+B)	-BA+9876+5*4*(32+1)
A109	17433	1-(-2-3^4)-5*-6+78*-9*(-A-B)	B+A+9876+5+432-1
A10A	17434	-1-23*-456+(-78-9)*(A-B)	B+A+9876+5+432*1
A10B	17435	1234-56+7*89*(A+B)	B*(A98-7+6-5-4-(-32-1))
A110	17436	(-1-(-2-3^4)*-5*6)*7/(8-9)+A-B	B+A-9*(8+7-6^5/4-3*2^1)
A111	17437	-1/-2*(3+(-4^5+6^7)/8+9)+A-B	BA+9+8+76*54*3-2*1
A112	17438	(-1-2-3-(-4-(5-6)^7))^8*9+A-B	B+A-9*8-7+6^5/4*3^2*1
A113	17439	1+(-2*3+(4+5-6)^7)*8-9+A-B	-BA9+8*(-7-(-6-54))^32*1
A114	17440	(-1*2^3+(4+5-6)^7)*8+9+A-B	BA+9+8+76*54*3+2-1
A115	17441	12345+6*(78-9A*B)	-B-A-9*(8-(7+6^5/4)+3)+2^1
A116	17442	1*-23*(456-7-89A-B)	-B-A-9-8*7*(6-5/4^3+2)^1
A117	17443	1-(2^3-(4+5-6)^7)*8+9-(A-B)	B+A98+7*(65+4)*(3+21)
A118	17444	1-(-2*(-3+4^5)-(-6-7)*8)*9-(A-B)	B+A+(9*8+7-6-5+4^3)^2-1
A119	17445	-1-(2+3-(4+5-6)^7)*8-9+A-B	BA+9876+5*-43*-2-1
A11A	17446	12-3+45-6-78*9*(A-B)	B*(-A9+87)*(-6-5-43+2-1)
A11B	17447	12345-(6+7*8*(-9A-B))	BA+9876-5*-43*2+1
A120	17448	(1-(2^3-(4+5-6)^7))^8*9+A-B	-BA-(-9876-543)+21
A121	17449	1^2-((-3^A-(4+5+6)+7)*8-9)+A-B	B+A+(-9*-8*-7+6)*-5*(4+3)-2/1
A122	17450	-1*(-2-3^4)*-5*-6*7+8-9+A+B	-B-A-9-8-7+6^5/4*3^2-1
A123	17451	1-23-45*-6*7+89AB	B+A-9*8+7+6^5/4*3^2-1
A124	17452	-12-3*-4+56+78*9*(A+B)	B+A-9-8*7+6^5/4*3^2^1
A125	17453	-1*(23-4)*567-(89+AB)	-BA9-87-6+543*21
A126	17454	(1-(2+3)+(4+5-6)^7)*8-9+A-B	B+A+9+(8+7+6*5*4-3)^2/1
A127	17455	1+2+3*-4-(-5+67)*(-89-AB)	B+A+9+(8+7+6*5*4-3)^2+1
A128	17456	-12+345+67*(89-A*-B)	B+A+9-8+(-7+6^5/4)/3^A-2+1
A129	17457	1+23*456-(-7-8-9A+B)	-B*(A98-(-76+54)+3+2)*-1
A12A	17458	-12*(-34-5-(-67+89A+B))	B+A9876+65*-4*(3+2-1)
A12B	17459	12345+6-7*8*(9A+B)	B+A-9*(8+7)+(-6*-5-4)^3-2-1
A130	17460	-1*-2*345*(6-7+8*(-9+A)+B)	B+A+9*(8+7+6+5^4)*3-2-1
A131	17461	1+2+(-3+4^5/(6-7))*(-8-9)+A-B	B+A+9*(8+7+6+5^4)*3-2^1
A132	17462	(-1-2+(3*(4-5)^6)^7)*8-9+A-B	B+A-9*(8-7-6^5/4+3+2)-1
A133	17463	1-(-23-45-(-6-78*-9*(A+B)))	B+A-9*(8-7-6^5/4+3+2^1)
A134	17464	(1-2*3+(4+5-6)^7)*8+9+A-B	-BA9-8-76-543*-21
A135	17465	-123-4-5*6*7*(-89+A+B)	-BA9-87+6-543*-21
A136	17466	-12+3-45*6*-7+89AB	BA*(-98-(-76-54-3))*(2+1)
A137	17467	1-((2+3-(4-(-5+6)^7))^8-9)-(A-B)	BA98-7-6*-5*(-43*2-1)
A138	17468	(-1-2*(3-(4^5-6*7)+8))^9+A-B	-B*(-A-(987+65+43*2*1))
A139	17469	-1*23*(4-(567-8)-(-9-AB))	B+A+9-8*(7-6*(5+4)^3/2)-1
A13A	17470	-1234+56+(7+8)*9A*B	-B+A987+65+43*-21
A13B	17471	-1*(-2/-3+4+5*6)*-7*8*9+A-B	BA9+8-76*-5*(-4+32+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A140	17472	$1*(-23+45)*6*(7-89*(A-B))$	$BA9+87*(65+43+21)$
A141	17473	$1-(2+3-45*6*7)+89AB$	$-BA9-8+7*6*(5-4)*-321$
A142	17474	$-1-23*-456-7-(-8-9-AB)$	$-B-A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/4-3+2^A1$
A143	17475	$(-1+2*3+4^5+6-7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A+98+765*4*(3+2-1)$
A144	17476	$(-1/2-(3-(4+5-6)^7))*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(6+5*(432+1))$
A145	17477	$1+2-3+45*6*-7+89AB$	$B+A-9*8*7*6+5*4^A(3^2^A1)$
A146	17478	$1+23-4+56+78*9*(-A-B)$	$-B+A9+8*-765*(4-3)*2*-1$
A147	17479	$1-2*(-3-4)-(-5+67)*(-89-AB)$	$B*(-A98-7*6*5+321)$
A148	17480	$-1*(-2+34)^9(567-89A+B)$	$-BA9+8-76+543*21$
A149	17481	$-123+4*56-78*9*(-A-B)$	$B+A+9*(8-7+6^A/4-3-2)^A1$
A14A	17482	$123+4*-5*(67-8*9A)+B$	$BA98-7-6+5*-432+1$
A14B	17483	$1+2-(-3-45*6*7-89AB)$	$B-A+9-(8*(765+4+3)*-2-1)$
A150	17484	$1^A2-3+(4+5-6)^A7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+6*(-5-3)*^2(2+1)$
A151	17485	$1-2+3^A(4+5-6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8-7+6^A/4*3^A2^A1$
A152	17486	$12-34*5*-67-8*(9+A)*-B$	$-B-A+9+8*7/6*5^A4*3-2^A1$
A153	17487	$1+(2+3*4-5-6)^A7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9/(8-7)*(-6^A/5/4+3)-2-1$
A154	17488	$-1-(2-34*-5-6)-(-7+8)*9*-AB$	$BA98-7-(-6+5*(432+1))$
A155	17489	$1+2+3^A(4+5-6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9/(8-7)*(-6^A/5/4+3)-2+1$
A156	17490	$1^A2+3+(4+5-6)^A7*8-9+A-B$	$B*(A98+7-(-65+43-2+1))$
A157	17491	$-1-(2-34-56)+78*-9*(-A-B)$	$-B-(-A987-6*54*3)-21$
A158	17492	$1234-(5-6+7*89*(-A-B))$	$B+A987+65-43*21$
A159	17493	$1+2*3+(4+5-6)^A7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(-6+5*432*1)$
A15A	17494	$12+3+45*6*7+89AB$	$BA98+7-6-5*432-1$
A15B	17495	$1+2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(8-7+6^A/5/-4-3)+2*1$
A160	17496	$-1*-23*(-456-(7+8-9))*(A-B)$	$BA+9876-5*4*(3-2-1)$
A161	17497	$1-2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6*5*43*2*-1$
A162	17498	$-1-2-3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(7+6*-5*43*-2-1)$
A163	17499	$-123-(4+5)-(-6-(-7-8)*9*-AB)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^A/5/4+3-2^A1)$
A164	17500	$-1*2*(-34-5*6)*(-7-8+9+AB)$	$BA98+7-6-5*(432-1)$
A165	17501	$-12-3*-456+7*(8+9)*AB$	$B*(-A+9)*(-8-7-6+54)*(-32+1)$
A166	17502	$1^A2-3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*-87-6*-5*(432+1)$
A167	17503	$-1-(-23+45*6*-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9*(8-7-6^A/5/4)-3*2+1$
A168	17504	$(1+2-3+4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-(-8+(7+6+5)^A/3)/-2*1$
A169	17505	$1+(2+3*4-5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA-987*-6+5432-1$
A16A	17506	$1+23*456+78-(9*-A+B)$	$-BA-987*-6-5432*-1$
A16B	17507	$1^A2*3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA-987*-6+5432+1$
A170	17508	$1^A2+3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7+6^A/5/4*3^A2+1$
A171	17509	$-123+4+(5+6+7)*(-8+9*A*B)$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4-3^A2+1$
A172	17510	$1+2+3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4-3*2-1$
A173	17511	$1+2*3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6*5*-43*-2*1$
A174	17512	$1*-2*(-3+45-6)*(-78-9A+B)$	$BA98-(-7-6)-5*(432-1)$
A175	17513	$-1-23*-456-(7+8)*9*(A+B)$	$BA-(-98-76*-54*-3)-21$
A176	17514	$(-1+2^A3^A4)*-5*(6-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4-3/(2-1)$
A177	17515	$1+2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4-3+2-1$
A178	17516	$(-1/-2*3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*-54*-3*(-2+1)$
A179	17517	$1234-5*6*7-89AB$	$-B+A987+6*-54*3+2-1$
A17A	17518	$12+34*56*7*8*(9-AB)$	$B+A+9-8+(7+6+5)^A/3/2/1$
A17B	17519	$1-2+(3+4)^A5-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9876+543-21$
A180	17520	$(1+2*3)^A4+5*6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+98*(76+54-3)+21$
A181	17521	$(1+2*3)^A4+5^A6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4+3+2-1$
A182	17522	$-123-4*5*-678-9AB$	$B+A-9+8+7+6^A/5/4*3^A2-1$
A183	17523	$-1*-23*(4+5+6*7*8+9+A-B)$	$-B*(A-98+765+432)*-1$
A184	17524	$1-2-34*-56*7+8*-9A-B$	$B-A987+654*(32+1)$
A185	17525	$-1+(2+3*(4+5-6)^A7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7+6^A/5/4*3^A2*1$
A186	17526	$12345-6*-7*(-8-9)*A-B$	$B+A+9^A(8-7)*6^A/5/4+3^A2^A1$
A187	17527	$-1-2-(-3456+7*8*(9+A)*-B)$	$B+A+9+8-7+6^A/5/4*3^A2^A1$
A188	17528	$12*(-3+45-67+89A+B)$	$-BA9+8-7*6+543*21$
A189	17529	$1^A2+(3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A*(9-87-65*(4-3-21))$
A18A	17530	$-123+45*-6*7*8-(9A-B)$	$B+A-9-8*7+(6+5*4)^A3-2/1$
A18B	17531	$(1+2)^A3+(4+5-6)^A7*8+9+A-B$	$-BA9-(-8+7*-6*(5-4+321))$
A190	17532	$1*(-2-345)*(-6+78+9-AB)$	$-B-A+9*876-5*4*3*-21$
A191	17533	$-12-3456+789*(A+B)$	$-B+A+9876-5*4*(-32+1)$
A192	17534	$1+23*456+78-(-9A+B)$	$-B*(-A-(-98+765)-432+1))$
A193	17535	$1+23*(45+67)+89A*B$	$B-A-(-987*6+5*4*-321)$
A194	17536	$(1^A2+3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA+98-(-76*-54*-3+2*1)$
A195	17537	$-1*-2*(3-(-4^A5+6*7+8)*9)+A-B$	$BA+98+76*54*3-2+1$
A196	17538	$1+(-2+(-3-4)^A5)*-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6*54*3*2-1)$
A197	17539	$((1+2)^A(3+4)+5+6+7)*8+9-A*B$	$-B+A+9876+543-21$
A198	17540	$(-1-(-2^A3*-4-(5^A6+7))/8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6*-54*3-2*-1$
A199	17541	$1+23*(456+7)-(-8+9)*(A-B)$	$-B-(A-9876)-(-543+2+1)$
A19A	17542	$(1+2*3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7)*(6^A/5/4+3)-2^A1$
A19B	17543	$1-23*-456-7+89-A*-B$	$-B-A+9876+543-2+1$
A1A0	17544	$-1-2-(3456-789*(A+B))$	$BA+9876-5+432-1$
A1A1	17545	$1-(-2-(3^A(-4-(-5-6))^7)*8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9876-5-432*-1$
A1A2	17546	$1*(2+3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8+9-(A-B)$	$BA+9876-5+432+1$
A1A3	17547	$-1-23*-456+78-9A+AB$	$-B-A+9876+543+2+1$
A1A4	17548	$1*2*(-34-5+6+7*(89A-B))$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5*4)^A3-2/1$
A1A5	17549	$1+23*456-(-78+9-AB)$	$BA+98*(76+54)-321$
A1A6	17550	$1*(2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A+9-8+76*(-54*-3+2+1)$
A1A7	17551	$1+(2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5*4)^A3+2-1$
A1A8	17552	$12-34-56*7*(8-9-A-B)$	$B+A+9-8*7+(6+5*4)^A3+2/1$
A1A9	17553	$-1-2-3*4*(-5+6)*(7+8+9A)*-B$	$-BA9-8-7+6-543*-21$
A1AA	17554	$1-23*45*-6*7*(-89A-B)$	$BA+9876+5+432-1$
A1AB	17555	$1*-23+4+56*7*(-8-(-9-A-B))$	$BA+9876+5+432*1$
A1B0	17556	$12*-3*(45+678-9AB)$	$BA+9876+5+432+1$
A1B1	17557	$-1-(-2*-3*-4+5^A6+7)/-8*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8-7-6+543*21$
A1B2	17558	$(1+2^A3+(4+5-6)^A7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876)+5*-43*(-2-1)$
A1B3	17559	$1-(-2*-3*-4+5^A6+7)/-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*6*(5+4^A3/2)^A1$
A1B4	17560	$1*2*(-345+6*7-89)*(A-B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*7+(-6-5^A4)*3)-2*1$
A1B5	17561	$-123+45-6+(7+8)*-9*-AB$	$B+A+9876+543-21$
A1B6	17562	$-1+23*456-7+89+AB$	$-B+A+9876-(-543-2*-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A1B7	17563	$1 - (-2 - ((3^{\wedge}(-4 - (-5 - 6))) + 7) * 8 + 9)) + A - B$	$-B + A + 9876 + 543 - 2 + 1$
A1B8	17564	$(-1 * (2 / (-3 - 4) - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 + 543 + 2 * -1$
A1B9	17565	$-12 - 34 - 56 + (-7 - 8) * 9 * -AB$	$B - A + 9876 - (-543 + 2) + 1$
A1BA	17566	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 * (4 + 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 - 543 * (-2 + 1)$
A1BB	17567	$1 * 2^{\wedge}3 * (4 + 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 + 543 + 2 - 1$
A200	17568	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 * (4 + 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7 + 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B - A + 9876 + 543 - 2 * -1$
A201	17569	$1 + (2^{\wedge}3 + (4 + 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7) * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-BA9 + 8 - (7 - 6) + 543 * 21$
A202	17570	$-12 * (3 + 4 * -5 + 6 - 789 - AB)$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1$
A203	17571	$-1 * (-2 * (-3 + 4^{\wedge}5 - 6 * 7) + 8) * 9 + A + B$	$-BA9 + 8 - (-7 + 6) - 543 * -21$
A204	17572	$-1 + (-2 / (-3 - 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1$
A205	17573	$(-1 * 2 / (-3 - 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 / (2 - 1)$
A206	17574	$1 + (-2 / (-3 - 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1$
A207	17575	$-1 * 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B - (-A - 9876) + 5 * -4 * -32 * 1$
A208	17576	$-1 + 23 * (456 + 7 - 8 + 9 - A + B)$	$B + A + 9876 - 5 * -4 * 32 + 1$
A209	17577	$-1 * 23 * (-456 - (-7 + 8 + 9 + A - B))$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * (7 / 6 - 5 * (4 + 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
A20A	17578	$1 - 23 * -456 + 7 + 89 + AB$	$-B * (-A98 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 - 3 - 21)$
A20B	17579	$1 * 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + ((-9 + 8) * -7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4) * 3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
A210	17580	$1 + 2 + (-3 - (-4^{\wedge}5 - 6) + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 * 8 * (8 - 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3 * 2)^{\wedge}1$
A211	17581	$-1 - (-2 / (-3 * -4 + 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 * 8 - 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 * 3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
A212	17582	$-1 / -2 * 3 - (-4 + 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 * 3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
A213	17583	$-1 / 2 + 3 - (-4 + 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$-BA9 - (-8 - 7) + 6 + 543 * 21$
A214	17584	$1 * 2 * (-3 - 45) * (67 - 89 - AB)$	$BA98 + 76 + 5 * 432 * -1$
A215	17585	$1 - (-2 - 345 * 6) - (7 + 89) * -AB$	$B - (-A - 9876) - (-543 + 2) + 1$
A216	17586	$1 - 2 * (-3 - 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 * 7 + 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A - (-9876 - 543) * (2 - 1)$
A217	17587	$1 * 2 - ((-3 + 4) * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9876 - (-543 - 2 + 1)$
A218	17588	$1 / -2 * 3 + (-4 - (5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B + A9876 + 5 * 4 * 3 * (-2 - 1)$
A219	17589	$1 + (-2 / (-3 * -4 - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$BA98 + 76 + 5 * (-432 + 1)$
A21A	17590	$1 - 2 - 345 * -6 * (7 + 8 - 9) + AB$	$-B + A987 - 65 * (-4 * -3 - 2 * -1)$
A21B	17591	$12 - (-3 - (-4 + 567 * (-8 + 9 + A + B)))$	$B - A + 9876 - (-543 - 21)$
A220	17592	$-1 + 23 * 4 * (5 * 6 + 7 - (-8 - 9A)) - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 * 5 - 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1$
A221	17593	$1 / 2 + 3 + (-4 - (5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 * 1$
A222	17594	$(-1 + 2 - 3 - (-4^{\wedge}5 - 6 - 7)) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 + 1$
A223	17595	$-12 - 34 * 5 * (-67 - 8) + (-9 - A) * -B$	$B + A + 9 * 8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 * 3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
A224	17596	$1 + (-2 / (-3 - 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / -8 * 9 + A + B$	$-BA9 - 8 + 7 * 6 - 543 * -21$
A225	17597	$-1 * 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A + B$	$B + A + 9 * 8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 * 3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
A226	17598	$12 * (34 - 56 - (7 + 8 + 9A * -B))$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 - 3 * 2)^{\wedge}1$
A227	17599	$1 / 2 - (-3 * -4 + 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 * 5 + 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 / 1$
A228	17600	$-1 * -2 * -34 * (-5 + 6 - 78 - 9A - B)$	$B * -A * (-98 + 7 - (-6 - 5 * -4 + 32 - 1))$
A229	17601	$1 - 2 * 34 * (-5 - (-6 + 78 + 9A + B))$	$B + A - 9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}1$
A22A	17602	$1 * -2 * (345 + 6 + 78 * (9 + A * -B))$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1$
A22B	17603	$1 + 2 + (-3 - 4 + 5) * (67 - 8 + 9) * -A * B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}1$
A230	17604	$-1 * -23 * 4 * (-56 - 7 - (-89 - AB))$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1$
A231	17605	$-1 - 2 - 3 * (-456 - 7 - 8) * 9 - AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}1$
A232	17606	$1 - (-2 - ((-3 + 4) * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / 8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1$
A233	17607	$1 / -2 - (-3 - (-4 + 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}1$
A234	17608	$-1 * (-23 - 4) * (56 * 7 + 89 - A + B)$	$-BA * (98 - 76 + 5) * -4 + 3 - 2 - 1$
A235	17609	$1 * 2 - ((-3 + 4) * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 * 9 + A + B$	$-BA9 - 87 - (6 + 543) * -21$
A236	17610	$1 + 23 + 4 + 567 * (-8 + 9 - (A - B))$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 + 1$
A237	17611	$(-1^{\wedge}(2 + 3) + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9876 - (-543 - 21)$
A238	17612	$12 * (3 + 45 - 67 + 89A + B)$	$B + A + (9 + 8 + 7) * (6 - (-5 - 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2) - 1$
A239	17613	$123 * (4 + 56 + 7 - 89 + AB)$	$B + A + (9 + 8 + 7) * (6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 * 1)$
A23A	17614	$-1 * 2 + (3 + 4)^{\wedge}5 - 6 * (-7 - 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * 7 * (6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2 - 1)$
A23B	17615	$1 + 2 * -3 * -456 + 7 + 89 * AB$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * -7 * (-6 - 5 * -4^{\wedge}3) + 2 - 1$
A240	17616	$-1 + 2345 - 67 + 89 * AB$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * -7 * (-6 - 5 / -4^{\wedge} - 3) + 2 * 1$
A241	17617	$-1 + 2 - 3 * (456 + 78) * (-9 - (A - B))$	$B + A + 9 * 8 - 7 * (-6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$
A242	17618	$1 - (-2345 - (-67 - 89 * -AB))$	$-B - (A98 + 76 + 543 * -21)$
A243	17619	$1 - 2 - 3 + 4 - 56 + (7 + 8) * 9 * AB$	$-B + A * 98 - 76 * (54 - 3) * (-2 - 1)$
A244	17620	$-1 * 2^{\wedge}3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1$
A245	17621	$12 - 3 * (-4 - 5 * -6) - (7 + 8) * -9 * AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 * (2 - 1)$
A246	17622	$-12 + 3 * (-4 + 567) + 89AB$	$B * (A98 + 76 + 5 - (43 + 2 * -1))$
A247	17623	$-1 * (2 + 3 + (-4^{\wedge}5 - 6 - 7) * (8 + 9)) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}1$
A248	17624	$(-1 / -2 + 3^{\wedge}4) * -5 * -6 * (7 * 8 - 9) + A - B$	$-BA9 + 8 * 7 + 6 - 543 * -21$
A249	17625	$12 + 34 * (56 - 7) + 89AB$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 - 3 / (2 - 1))$
A24A	17626	$1 - (-2 - ((-3 + 4) * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / 8) * 9 + A + B$	$B + A - 9 * 8 * (-7 * -6 - 5 / 4) * -3 * 2 + 1$
A24B	17627	$1 / (2 - 3) + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B - (A + 987 * -6) - 5432 * -1$
A250	17628	$-123 + 45 * -6 * 7 * -8 + 9 * (A - B)$	$-BA9 - 9 - (8 + 7 * -65 * (-4 + 32 - 1))$
A251	17629	$1^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A - 98 * 7 - 6 * 5 * -432 * 1$
A252	17630	$1 - 2 + 3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8 * ((7 + 6 / (5 - 4))^{\wedge}3 + 2 + 1)$
A253	17631	$-1 - (-2 + 34 * (56 + 7 * -8 * 9)) + A * B$	$B + A - (-9 - 8 + (-7 - 6^{\wedge}5 / 4) * 3) * (2 + 1)$
A254	17632	$1 - (2 + (-3 - 4)^{\wedge}5) + (-6 - 7) * -8 * 9 - A * B$	$-B - A + 9 * 8 + 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 * 1$
A255	17633	$1 * 2 + 3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B * (A98 - (76 - 5 * -432) + 1)$
A256	17634	$1 + 2 + 3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$BA - 9 * 87 + 6 * 5 * 432 - 1$
A257	17635	$1 - 2 + 3 * (-4 + 567) + 89AB$	$B + A - (-9 * (-8 * -7 + 6^{\wedge}5) / 4 + 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
A258	17636	$12 + 3 + 45 * -6 * 7 * -8 + 9 * (-A - B)$	$B + A + (-9 - 8) * -7 - 6^{\wedge}5 / -4 * 3^{\wedge}2 * 1$
A259	17637	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9 * (-8 * -7 + 6^{\wedge}5) / 4 - 3 / 2^{\wedge} - 1$
A25A	17638	$(-1 - 2 - 3^{\wedge}4) * -5 * 6 * 7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 * (8 * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5) / 4 - 3 - 2^{\wedge}1$
A25B	17639	$1 + 2 - (-3 * (-4 + 567) - 89AB)$	$-B + A + 9 * 8 * 7 * (-6 - 5 + 4) * (3 * -2 + 1)$
A260	17640	$12 * 3 * -4 * 5 * (-6 - (-78 + 9A - B))$	$B - A98 - 76 + 543 * 21$
A261	17641	$-1 + 2 + 34 * (-5 - 67 + 89) * (A + B)$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1$
A262	17642	$1 + (-2 + 3 + 4 + 5 * 6) * -7 * 8 * -9 - (A - B)$	$B + A - 9 + 8 * 7 + (6 + 5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 / 1$
A263	17643	$-1 - 2 * -3456 - 7 * 8 * (-9 + A + B)$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 - 3 + 2)^{\wedge}1$
A264	17644	$-1 * (-234 - (5 - (6 - 7 - 89A))) * B$	$-BA9 - 8 + 76 - 543 * -21$
A265	17645	$1 - 23 * (-456 - 7) + (-8 - (-9 - A)) * B$	$-BA9 + 8 + 76 * -5 * (-4 - 32 - 1)$
A266	17646	$1 + (-2 + 3 + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B + A + 987 * 6 - (-5432 + 1)$
A267	17647	$(1^{\wedge}(2 - 3) + 4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) - (A - B)$	$-B + A + 987 * 6 + 5432 * 1$
A268	17648	$123 - 45 * 6 * -7 + 89AB$	$-B + A987 + 6 * -5 * (4 - 32) * -1$
A269	17649	$1 * (234 + 5) * (67 + 89 - AB)$	$B - A - 987 * -6 - 5432 * -1$
A26A	17650	$1 * (2 - 3 * 4) * (-56 * -7 - (-8 - 9) * -A + B)$	$B - A + 987 * 6 + 5432 + 1$
A26B	17651	$1^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}3 + (4^{\wedge}5 + 6 + 7) * (8 + 9) + A + B$	$BA98 - 765 + 4 * -321$
A270	17652	$-1 + 23 - (45 + 6 + (-7 - 8) * 9 * AB)$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2) * 1$
A271	17653	$-1 + 2345 + 6 * -7 + 89 * AB$	$B + A + 9 * (8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2) + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A272	17654	$-1+23*(456+7)-8+9+AB$	$B+A*(-9*(8+7+6^5/4+3^5-2)-1)$
A273	17655	$1-(2-(-3-4^5-6-(7+8)*-9*AB))$	$-B*(-A98-7-(6+54-3)+21)$
A274	17656	$1+23*(456+7)-8+9+AB$	$B+A*987-6*(5-432)+1$
A275	17657	$-1-2+3*(4+567)+89AB$	$-B+A*(-98+7)*(6^5-5-43)*2*-1$
A276	17658	$1-2*-3*(-4-5-6*-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*-7-6^5/-4*3)*(2+1)$
A277	17659	$(1+2+3)^4*((-5+6*7)/8+9)-(A-B)$	$-BA9+87-6-543*-21$
A278	17660	$(-1-2-3^4)*-5*6*7+8-9+A+B$	$-BA9+87+6-543*-21$
A279	17661	$-1+2-3*(-4-567)+89AB$	$B-A9-8+7*65*(-4+32-1)$
A27A	17662	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)*(-5*-6*7-8*9)+A-B$	$-BA-98*-76-5+4321$
A27B	17663	$-1*-2^{\wedge}(3+4)*(-5*-6*7-8*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7+(6+5*4)^3+2-1$
A280	17664	$-1-23-(4-5)-(-6-(-7-8)*-9*AB)$	$B+A+9+8*7+(6+5*4)^3+2/1$
A281	17665	$(1-(2-3+4)^5)*(6-(7+8*9))+A-B$	$-B+A987-654+3*-21$
A282	17666	$1*(234-5+6+7+89A)*B$	$B*(A98-(-7-65)-(-4+32)*1)$
A283	17667	$(1^{\wedge}(2-3)+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$BA98-7*-6*(-54-3-2)+1$
A284	17668	$-12*(-345+67-8*(9A-B))$	$B+A*(-987*6-5432+1)$
A285	17669	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3^4)*-5*(-6*7-8*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9*8-7(-7-6(-5-4)*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
A286	17670	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5+6+7)*8+9+A+B$	$B+A-987*-6+5432+1$
A287	17671	$1+2-345-678*(-9-A)-B$	$-BA9+87+6-543*-21$
A288	17672	$-12-3-4*(5-6)+(7+8)*-9*-AB$	$-BA+98*76+5+4321$
A289	17673	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5*6+7)*8-9-A*B$	$-B+A98-7*-6*54*3*2*-1$
A28A	17674	$1-23-(-4-5)+6-(-7-8)*9*AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6+5*4)^3-2*1$
A28B	17675	$1-2*345-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6+5*4)^3-2+1$
A290	17676	$-12-3-4*5*-678-9AB$	$BA+987*6-5*4*-321$
A291	17677	$-1*(2+(-3-(4^5+6+7))*(8+9))+A-B$	$B*(A98-(7+6)-(-54-3+2)-1)$
A292	17678	$-1/-2*(-3*-4^5+6^7)/8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6+5*4)^3+2*1$
A293	17679	$-1-2*(-3-4)+(5+6)*(7*8+9*A)*B$	$-BA98-7+6*5*43*-21$
A294	17680	$-12+3456-78*(-9A-B)$	$B+A-9*(-8*-7*-6+5+4)*3*2+1$
A295	17681	$(1-2+3)^4*-5*(-6-7)*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A-(-9*(-8*-7+6^5)/4+3^2)+1$
A296	17682	$12-345+678*(9A)-B$	$BA+9876-(-543+21)$
A297	17683	$(1-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^7+8+9-A*B$	$B+A-9+8*(7+6-5*4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
A298	17684	$1+2345-6-7-89*-AB$	$B+A-9+8*(7+6-5*4*3)^{\wedge}2/1$
A299	17685	$-1*(-2-3)*4-(-5+6)*(7-8)*-9*AB$	$B+A-9+8*(7+6-5*4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
A29A	17686	$(-1-2*(3-4^5+6*7)+8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9*-8*(7/-6+5)*4^3+2-1$
A29B	17687	$(-1-(-2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)*6)*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-654+3*-21$
A2A0	17688	$-1*(-234+56*7)*8-(9+AB)$	$B*(A98+76+5-(4+32)-1)$
A2A1	17689	$(-1-2*-3*(4+5))*-6*-7*8-9-A*B$	$B+A+(-9+8-7)*(-6-5^4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
A2A2	17690	$12-3-45*6*-7*8-9A-B$	$B+A+9-8-7*(-6-5^4)*(3+2-1)$
A2A3	17691	$-1-2-(-3456-78*(9A+B))$	$B+A+(-9/((-8+(-7*6-(5-4))^3)*2))^{\wedge}-1$
A2A4	17692	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7-8-9-A*B$	$B+A+(9+8+7)*((-6-5)^4-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
A2A5	17693	$1-(2-3456+78*(-9A-B))$	$-BA98+7-6*-5*43*21$
A2A6	17694	$-1+2345+6-7-89*-AB$	$B+A+9+8*((7*6+5^4(4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
A2A7	17695	$-1-2345*(6-7)-89*-AB$	$-B-A98-(7+6)-543*-21$
A2A8	17696	$1+2345+6-7-89*-AB$	$BA+9876+5*4*-32*-1$
A2A9	17697	$1+2+3456-78*(-9A-B)$	$BA+9876+5*-4*-32+1$
A2AA	17698	$1+2345-6+7+89*AB$	$B+A+9+8*7*(6+5^4)/(3-2+1)$
A2AB	17699	$-1*(2+(-3-(4^5+6+7))*(8+9))+A+B$	$B+A+(-9+(8+(7+6)^5)/(4+3))/(2+1)$
A2B0	17700	$-1/-2*(-3*-4^5+6^7)/8-9+A+B$	$-BA+98*(76+54)+3-21$
A2B1	17701	$(1-2+3)^4*-5*(-6-7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-654-32-1$
A2B2	17702	$1234+5*6+7+89AB$	$-B+A987-(654-32*-1)$
A2B3	17703	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6-6-(7-8)^{\wedge}9-A*B$	$-B+A987-(654+32-1)$
A2B4	17704	$12-3-4*-5*678-9AB$	$BA-(-9876-543)-2-1$
A2B5	17705	$-1+23-45*-6*7*8-9A-B$	$BA-(-9876-(543+2*-1))$
A2B6	17706	$(-1-2*(3-4^5+6*7)+8)*9+A+B$	$BA+9876+543-(2-1)$
A2B7	17707	$-1+23*456+(-7*-8+9*-A)*-B$	$-B-A98-7+6-543*-21$
A2B8	17708	$-1+2345+6-(-7-89*AB)$	$BA+9876-(-543-2+1)$
A2B9	17709	$(-1-(-2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)*6)*(7+8+9)+A+B$	$BA+9876-(-543-2*1)$
A2BA	17710	$1*(-2+3*-45*-6-789)*-A*B$	$B*(-A-9*(-87-65))^*(-4+3+2)*1$
A2BB	17711	$-1*2*-3*(-4+5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8-7+6*5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
A300	17712	$1-2*-3*(-4+5-6*7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-654-3-21$
A301	17713	$(-1+2*3+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*-7-((-6-5*4)^3+2+1)$
A302	17714	$1+2-3*(-45-6)*78+9AB$	$B+A+(-9*(-8-7*6*5)+4)*3^{\wedge}2-1$
A303	17715	$(-1*-2*(-3+4^5-6*7)+8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9*(-8+7*-6*5)+4)*3^{\wedge}2A1$
A304	17716	$-1-(23-(45+6-(-7-8)*9*AB))$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*(6-5*(-4^3+2))-1)$
A305	17717	$-1*-2^{\wedge}3*-4*(5+(-6-7*8)*9)+A+B$	$B+A+(-9*(-8*-7+6)+5)*4^3/-2*1$
A306	17718	$-1/-2*(-3*-4^5+6^7)/8+9+A+B$	$-B-(-A987+654-3+21)$
A307	17719	$(1-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^7+8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-65*-4*-3-21$
A308	17720	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3+(4+5-6)^{\wedge}7)*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(-8*(-7-6)^5/4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
A309	17721	$1+23+4*5*678-9AB$	$-B-A98+7+6+543*21$
A30A	17722	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^5+(-6-7)*-8*9-(A+B)$	$-BA+98*7*(-6-(5+4-32)-1)$
A30B	17723	$((-1-2)*-3*-4+5/6)*-7*8*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+654+32)-1$
A310	17724	$-12*(34-5-(-6*-7+89A-B))$	$B-(-A987+654-32*-1)$
A311	17725	$1+2+(3+4)^5+(-6-7)*-8*9-(A+B)$	$B+A987-654-32+1$
A312	17726	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6+7+8+9-A*B$	$B+A+9-8*7*(6-5*4^3-2)^{\wedge}1$
A313	17727	$(-1-(2-3^4))*(-5*-6*7+8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A-9*(-8+7*6)*(5-4^3+2-1)$
A314	17728	$1+234+5+6+78*-9*(-A-B)$	$-BA-987-6-543*-21$
A315	17729	$-1+(-2*-3+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-A98-(7-6)-543*-21$
A316	17730	$-1*(-234-56)*(7+8+9+A+B)$	$B+A+9-(-8-7*(6+5^4))^*(3+2-1)$
A317	17731	$1+(-2*-3+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-(A98-(7-6)-543*21)$
A318	17732	$-1+23-45*-6+78*-9*(-A-B)$	$BA-(-9876-543)+21$
A319	17733	$-1*2*-3*(-4+5-6*7)*-8*9+A+B$	$-B+A987-654+3*-2-1$
A31A	17734	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6-7-8*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987-654-3*2*1$
A31B	17735	$(-1+2*3+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-654-(-3*-2-1)$
A320	17736	$1+(2+3+4^5+6+7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-654-3-2+1$
A321	17737	$-1+2345+6*7+89*AB$	$-B-A+(-9-8/-7*(6^5+4-3))/2^{\wedge}-1$
A322	17738	$(1-2^{\wedge}3+4)^5*(6-7-8*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-654-(3-2+1)$
A323	17739	$-1*-23*(456-78-(-9A+B))$	$-B+A987-654-3+2*1$
A324	17740	$-1*2+(3+4)^5+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-654-3+2+1$
A325	17741	$1-(2+(-3-4)^5)+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-654+3+2*-1$
A326	17742	$1^{\wedge}2*(3+4)^5+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-654+3-2+1$
A327	17743	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^5+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B-(A98-7-6-543*21)$
A328	17744	$-12+3+4+56-(-7-8)*9*AB$	$-B+A987-654+3+2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A329	17745	$1+2+(3+4)^5+(-6-7)^*-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(654-(3-2^*-1))$
A32A	17746	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987-654+3^*-2^*-1$
A32B	17747	$(-1+2^3+4^5+6+7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+654-3^*2)+1$
A330	17748	$1-2-(34^*-56^*7-8^*-9^*A+B)$	$BA98-7-654^*3-21$
A331	17749	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7^*8-9^*A^*B$	$-B+A987-654-3^*(-2-1)$
A332	17750	$-1^*(-2+3-(-4-56))^*(7^*(-8-9))-AB$	$-BA^*(-9-(8+7+65-4)-(3+21))$
A333	17751	$-1+(-2^*-3+4^5+6+7)^*(8+9)+A+B$	$BA-98^*7+6^*-5^*-432+1$
A334	17752	$-12^*(-3-(-4-56-78+9AB))$	$-B+A9^*87+6^*(543-21)$
A335	17753	$1+(-2^*-3+4^5+6+7)^*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A+(9^*8+7)^*((-6+5-4)^3)^2-1$
A336	17754	$-1^*-2^*(-3-(-4-(-567-8)))+9-A)^*-B$	$-B^*(-A98-7+6-54+3^*2+1)$
A337	17755	$(1-(2-3^*4+5)^6)/-7^*8+9-A^*B$	$B+A987-654-3^*2-1$
A338	17756	$(-1-2^*(3-4^5+6)-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+654)-(3-(-2-1))$
A339	17757	$-12+3^*4^5+6^*7+89AB$	$B+A987-(654-3^*2-1)$
A33A	17758	$-1^*2^*(-3+4+5-(6+7^*89A-B))$	$B+A987-(654+3+2)+1$
A33B	17759	$(-1/-2+3^4)^*(-5^*-6^*7+8)-9-(A-B)$	$B+A987-654-3^*(2-1)$
A340	17760	$-1^*-2^*34^*(56+(-7-8))^*-9+A+B$	$B-(-A987+654+3-2+1)$
A341	17761	$-1+23^*(-4-5)^*-67-8-9AB$	$B+A987-654-3+2^*1$
A342	17762	$1^*2^*(-34+56+7^*(89A)^*B)$	$-B+A987-654-3+21$
A343	17763	$-1+(-2^3-4^5-(6+7))^*(-8-9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+654^*(3-2)-1)$
A344	17764	$-1+2^*(3+4)+56-(-7-8)^*-9^*-AB$	$B+A987-654-(-3+2)+1$
A345	17765	$1+(2^3+4^5+6+7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B^*(-A98-76+5+43-21)$
A346	17766	$1^*-2^*(-345+67-8-9)^*(A+B)$	$B-(-A987+654-3-(2-1))$
A347	17767	$1+2^*(3+4)^*(-56-78+9AB)$	$B+A987-654+3-2^*-1$
A348	17768	$(-1-2^*3^4)^*(5-6^*7-8^*9)-(A-B)$	$B+A987-(654+3^*2^*-1)$
A349	17769	$(-1+2^3+4^5+6+7)^*(8+9)+A+B$	$B+A987-654+3^*2+1$
A34A	17770	$-1^*-2^*(3+4567-8+9^*AB)$	$BA98-7-654^*3-(2+1)$
A34B	17771	$-123-45^*-67-89^*-AB$	$B+A+(-9^*-8-7+6)^*5^4/(3/2+1)$
A350	17772	$(-1/-2+3^4-5^6)/-7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(7-654^*-3)-2+1$
A351	17773	$-1+(-2+3^4)^*-5^*(-6-(7-8))^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654^*3^*(2-1)$
A352	17774	$-1+2345-(-67-89^*AB)$	$BA98-76^*(5+43-21)$
A353	17775	$-1^*(-2345-(67+89^*AB))$	$BA98-7+654^*-3-2^*-1$
A354	17776	$-1^*(-234-(5-(-6-7-89A)))^*B$	$-B^*-A-9^*-8^*(7/-6+5)^*4^3+2/1$
A355	17777	$-12+34+56+(7+8)^*9^*AB$	$-B-(-A987+654)+32-1$
A356	17778	$-123-4^*-56+(-7-8)^*9^*-AB$	$-B+A987-654-32^*-1$
A357	17779	$-1^*(23-4)^*(-567-89+AB)$	$-B+A987-654-(-32-1)$
A358	17780	$-1^*(2-34^*5-(-67+8))^*(9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8/-7^*(6^5+4-3))^*2+1$
A359	17781	$1+2^*-3^*(-456+7)+89A^*B$	$BA9-87^*(6-5^*4)^*3^*-2^*1$
A35A	17782	$((1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7)^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8^*-7^*(6-5^*(-4^3+2)+1)$
A35B	17783	$((-1+2+3+4)^*-5^*-6+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8/-7^*(6^5^*-4+3)/2-1$
A360	17784	$123^*(-45-67-(-89-AB))$	$B+A987-654-3+21$
A361	17785	$1^*-2^*(-3-4^*5^6)/7-8^*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+654^*-3-2^*1$
A362	17786	$1-2^*(-3-4^*5^6)/7-8^*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-654^*-3)-(2-1)$
A363	17787	$-1+23^*-4^*(-56+7)-8^*-9AB$	$-B^*(-A9-87-654-321)$
A364	17788	$(-1-2^*3^4)^*(5-6^*7-8^*9)+A+B$	$BA98-(-7-654^*-3-2)-1$
A365	17789	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8-9-(A-B)$	$BA-987^*-6+5432-1$
A366	17790	$1^*2^*(-3+4567+8+9^*AB)$	$B-(-A987+654)-(-3-21)$
A367	17791	$(1-2-3)^(4+5)+6^7/(-8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A+9+8)-7^*-65^*(-4+32-1)$
A368	17792	$(1-2-3)^(4+5)+6^7/8-9+A-B$	$-BA9-8+7^*654^*3+21$
A369	17793	$1-(23+45^*6^*7^*8)-(-9+A)^*B$	$-B-A+98^*76+5+4321$
A36A	17794	$(-1/-2+3^4-5^6)/-7^*8+9+A+B$	$-B^*-A+(9-(8+(7+6)^5)/(-4-3))/(2+1)$
A36B	17795	$-1+(-2+3^4)^*-5^*(-6-(7-8))^*9+A+B$	$B+A+(9^*8+7)^*((-6+5-4)^3)^2-1$
A370	17796	$(1-2-3)^(4+5)+6^7/8-9+A+B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*4^3+2-1)$
A371	17797	$(-1/-2+3^4)^*(-5^*-6^*7+8)+9+A+B$	$B+A+(9^*8+7)^*((-6+5-4)^3)^2+1$
A372	17798	$1^*-2+3+45^*-6^*7^*8+(-9+A)^*-B$	$BA98-7+654^*-3+21$
A373	17799	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8+9-A-B$	$B+A987-654+32-1$
A374	17800	$((1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7)^*8+9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+654-32^*1)$
A375	17801	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A987-654+32+1$
A376	17802	$-1+23^*-45+6+78^*(9A)^*B$	$-BA+9876+(5-43)^*-21$
A377	17803	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*4^3)-2/1$
A378	17804	$1^*2^*(-3-4-5^*-6+7^*89A-B)$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7-6)^*(5-4^*3^*2)-1$
A379	17805	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*8^*(7+6^*5^4^3/2)^1$
A37A	17806	$(-1-2^3)^*-4-5^6/7-7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7-6)^*(5-4^*3^*2)+1$
A37B	17807	$1^*-2^*(-3-4^*5^6)/7-8^*9+A+B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*4^3)+2^1$
A380	17808	$-12^*(-3-4-5-(-6+7)-89A+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5/-4^3)+2+1$
A381	17809	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8-9+A+B$	$B+A987-6-5^*(4+3)^*21$
A382	17810	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8)^9+A-B$	$-B-A+((9-8)^7+6)^5+4^3(3+2)^1$
A383	17811	$(1+2)^(3+4)-5^6+7-8)^9+A-B$	$BA+9876-5^*(4+3)^*-21$
A384	17812	$1+23^*(4+5)^*67+(8+9A)^*-B$	$BA987-(-654^*-3-21)$
A385	17813	$(1-2-3)^(4+5)+6^7/(-8+9)+A+B$	$BA-98+7^*65^*(-4+32-1)$
A386	17814	$1-2^*(3+(-4^5-(-6^*7+8)))^9)+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*(-7^*(-6^*5-4)+3^2)-1)$
A387	17815	$123+4-(-5+6+7)^*89^*(-A-B)$	$-B+A987-654-3^*-21$
A388	17816	$-1^*-2^*(3-45+6-(7+8)-9)^*-AB$	$B+A+9^*(-8+7^*6+5^4)^*3+2^*1$
A389	17817	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*(-8-(-7^*6-5^4))^*3+2+1$
A38A	17818	$1-2+3+(4-(-5-6+7))^*(-8-9)^*-AB$	$-B-A+9+(8-7+6)^5+4^3(3+2)-1$
A38B	17819	$-1+2^*(-3+4-5^*-6+7^*89A-B)$	$-B+A^*(987-(65-4)+321)$
A390	17820	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4)^*(567-8-(-9-A))^*B$	$B-A98+76+543^*21$
A391	17821	$1-23^*(4-(-56+78))^*(9+A+B)$	$BA98-7-6^*(-5+4+321)$
A392	17822	$-12^*(3-4-56+78-9A^*B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*4^3-2)-1$
A393	17823	$1-23^*-4^*(56-(7-89))^*A^*B$	$-B+A9-8^*-7^*-65^*-4+321$
A394	17824	$1-2^*((-3-4^*5^6)/7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^*-5^*4^3-2)+1$
A395	17825	$-1^*-2^*((-3-4^*5^6)/7-8-9)-(A-B)$	$B-(-A-98^*76)-(-5-4321)$
A396	17826	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7/(8-9)+A+B$	$-B-A-9^*((-8+7-6^*5)^*4^3+2-1)$
A397	17827	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7-8+9+A+B$	$B-(-A-98^*(76+54)+32^*1)$
A398	17828	$1-(-2-3-4^*5^*678)-9A^*B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*((7/-6+5)^*4^3+2)-1$
A399	17829	$-1-234+5-678^*(-9-A)-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*((7/-6+5)^*4^3+2^1)$
A39A	17830	$1^*(-2-(-3+4-5^6)/7)^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*((7/-6+5)^*4^3+2)+1$
A39B	17831	$-1+2345-67-89A^*-B$	$B+A^*9^*(87-6-54)^*-3^*-2^*1$
A3A0	17832	$1^*2345-67+89A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(8-7-6^*5^*(4^3+2)^1)$
A3A1	17833	$1+2345-67-89A^*-B$	$BA9-8+7^*-6^*5^4^*(3-(2+1))$
A3A2	17834	$(-1+(-2-3-4^*5)^*-6^*7)^*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*8^*(-7-6^*5^4+3)^*2-1$
A3A3	17835	$(1+2)^(3+4)+5^6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A-(-98^*76-5-4321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A3A4	17836	$12^*(3+4)*(-5-6+78-9-A^*B)$	$-B-A9^*-87-6^*-5^*4^*-32^*-1$
A3A5	17837	$((1+2)^3+3+4^*5)*(-6^*-7+8)^9+A^*B$	$B+A987-(654+3^*-21)$
A3A6	17838	$(-1+2+3+4-5^*6)/-7^*8-9+A^*B$	$B+A+9-8^*-7^*6^*(5+(4+3)^2-1)$
A3A7	17839	$123+45^*6^*-7^*-8-9-AB$	$B+A-9^*(-8-7)^*(-6-5)^*-4^*3-2^*1$
A3A8	17840	$-1^*(23+45)^*(6+7-89-AB)$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7)^*(-6-5^*4^*3)^*2-1$
A3A9	17841	$(1+2)^3+3+4+5^*6+7-8+9+A^*B$	$B+A^*(987-65+4+321)$
A3AA	17842	$(-1-2+(-3/-4+5^*6)/7)^8+9+A^*B$	$-B^*(-A98-(-7+65)-(-4-3)-(2+1))$
A3AB	17843	$1-234-5-678^*(-9-A)+B$	$B-(-A987+65^*(4+3^*2+1))$
A3B0	17844	$-1-2^*34^*-5^*6^*7-89^*AB$	$B+A-9-8^*(-7^*6+(5+4)^3)^*(-2-1)$
A3B1	17845	$12345+6^*7^*8^*(9-A)^*B$	$B+A+9^*8^*-7^*65^*-4+321$
A3B2	17846	$(1-(2-3^*4+5)^6)/-7^*8-9+A^*B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)^*(-7^*-6^*((-5-4)^3+2)-1)$
A3B3	17847	$-1^*23^*(-456+7-(-89+AB))$	$-B+A+(9^*-8^*-7+6)^*-5^*(-4-3)-2^*1$
A3B4	17848	$1-23^*(-456-(-7-89+AB))$	$BA98-7^*6^*54-3-21$
A3B5	17849	$((1+2)^3+4+5+6-7)^*(8+9)+A^*B$	$BA9+8-7^*-6^*-54^*3^*-2^*1$
A3B6	17850	$-12^*-3^*(45^*6-7-(8+9-AB))$	$B+A+9^*(8-7-6^*-5^*(4^3+2))^\wedge 1$
A3B7	17851	$1+2-(-3/-4+5^*6)/-7^*8-9+A^*B$	$B+A+((9-8)^\wedge 7+6)^\wedge 5+4^\wedge 4(3+2)-1$
A3B8	17852	$1+2+(-3-4)^*-5^*(6-7^*-8^*9)+A^*B$	$B+A+((9-8)^\wedge 7+6)^\wedge 5+4^\wedge 4(3+2)^\wedge 1$
A3B9	17853	$((1-2-3)^\wedge 4-5^*6)^*(7+8^*9)+A^*B$	$B+A-(-9-8)^*765-(432-1)$
A3BA	17854	$-1-2^*(-3-4^*-5^*6+7)^*-8^*9+A^*B$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)^*-4^*-3/2+1$
A3BB	17855	$1^*-2^*(-3-4^*-5^*6+7)^*-8^*9+A^*B$	$BA98+7^*(6+54-321)$
A400	17856	$-1+2-345^*(-6-7)-89^*A^*B$	$-B+A-9^*(-8+7-6^*5)^*4^3+2-1$
A401	17857	$1-2^*3^*(4-56)^*(-78-(-9-AB))$	$-B^*-A+(-9^*-8^*-7+6+5)^*-4/3^\wedge 2-1$
A402	17858	$(1+2)^\wedge (3+4)+5^*6+7^*8-9+A^*B$	$-BA+9^*-8^*(-7+6)^*-5^*(-43+2-1)$
A403	17859	$-1^*-2^*((-3-4^*5^*6)/-7-8+9)+A^*B$	$BA9-876^*(5+4+3-21)$
A404	17860	$1+23+4^*(-5^*-6^*7+8^*9^*AB)$	$B-A+9-(-8-7+6-5)^*-43^*-21$
A405	17861	$1-(-2+(-3+4-5^*6)/7)^8+9-A^*B$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6)^\wedge 5+4^\wedge 4(3+2^\wedge 1)$
A406	17862	$-1^*-2^*(34+5-6)^*(-7+89+AB)$	$BA98-7+65^*(4-32-1)$
A407	17863	$1-(-2-3/4+5^*6)/-7^*8+9+A^*B$	$-B-A+(-9^*-8+7-6)^*5^*(4+3)^2-1$
A408	17864	$-12^*(-3-4+5+6^*(-7+8)^*(-9-A))^*B$	$B^*(-A9-87)^*(6^*(-5+4)-(-3-2)^*1)$
A409	17865	$-12+345+6-78^*9^*(A-B)$	$-B-A+(-9^*-8+7-6)^*5^*(4+3)^2+1$
A40A	17866	$(-1+2+3^*4)^*(-5^*-6^*7+8)-9+A^*B$	$-B+A987-6-(543+21)$
A40B	17867	$((1^2+3)^\wedge 4+5/-6-7)^8+9+A^*B$	$-B-A-9^*-8^*(-7-6)^*(-5^*4-3^\wedge 2+1)$
A410	17868	$12345-6^*789-AB$	$BA-987+(-6+543)^*21$
A411	17869	$1+2-(-3/-4+5^*6)/-7^*8+9+A^*B$	$-B-(-A-(-987-6))-543^*-21$
A412	17870	$-12+34^*56-7+89AB$	$BA98-7^*6^*54-3^*-2^*-1$
A413	17871	$1^*(234-56-789)^*(A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*(-876-(543-21))$
A414	17872	$1^*2^*(3+456+78^*9^*A+B)$	$B+A+(-9^*-8^*-7-6)^*-5^*(4+3)+2-1$
A415	17873	$12345+6^*(-789-A-B)$	$B-A+987+7^*(65-4)^*-32^*-1$
A416	17874	$1^*-23^*(4-(-5+6^*(7+89)+A)+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7-6^*5)^*4^\wedge 3-(2+1)$
A417	17875	$1-2^*(-3-4^*5^*6)/7+8+9+A^*B$	$-B^*(-A98-76-5+4-3+21)$
A418	17876	$(1+2)^\wedge (3+4)+5^*6-7+8^*9+A^*B$	$BA98-7^*(-65+4+321)$
A419	17877	$((1/-2+3)^4+5^*6)^*-7/(8-9)+A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(8-(-7+65))^\wedge (4+3+21)$
A41A	17878	$-12^*(3-45-(-67+8+9^*AB))$	$-B+A987+6-543-21$
A41B	17879	$-1-2^*(3-(-4+5+6^*78))+9A^*B$	$-BA9-8+(7+6+543)^*21$
A420	17880	$(-1+((-2-3)^*-4+5^*6)/7)^8+9+A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7-6^*5)^*4^\wedge 3+2+1$
A421	17881	$1-(-2+(-3+4-5^*6)/7)^8+9+A^*B$	$-B+A-(987-6)+543^*21$
A422	17882	$((1+2^*3+4)^\wedge 5+(-6-7)^*8)/9+A^*B$	$-BA-9-876+543^*21$
A423	17883	$12+3^*-4^*(-56-78+9)^*A^*B$	$B-A-(987-6)+543^*21$
A424	17884	$-12-34^*-56+7+89AB$	$-B^*-A+(9^*8+7)^*((-6+5-4)^*3)^\wedge 2-1$
A425	17885	$-1+2-34^*-56-7+89AB$	$B+A+98^*(76+54)-(-3+2+1)$
A426	17886	$-1+2^*(34+5+678)^*9-AB$	$B^*(A-9+8^*7^*-6+54)^*3^*2^*-1$
A427	17887	$1+2-34^*-56-7+89AB$	$B-A+987-(-6+543)^*-21$
A428	17888	$((1+2^*3+4)^\wedge 5+6-7^*8)/9+A^*B$	$-B+A987+6^*-5^*(43-21)$
A429	17889	$12345-6^*789+A^*B$	$-B+A987-6+(543+2)^*-1$
A42A	17890	$123(-4-5^*6)-(-7-8)^*-9^*-AB$	$-B+A987-(6+543)-2+1$
A42B	17891	$(-1/-2-(-3+4+5)^*6)^*-7^*8^*9+A^*B$	$B+A-987-6+543^*21$
A430	17892	$12^*-3^*(-45^*6+7-8-9+AB)$	$BA^*(9-8)^*(76-(5-4)+32-1)$
A431	17893	$1-((-2-3)^*-4+5^*6)/-7^*8-9+A^*B$	$-B-A9-876-543^*-21$
A432	17894	$-1+2+(34-5)^*6^*78-9AB$	$-B+A987-(6+543)+2+1$
A433	17895	$1+234^*5-(6-78)^*-9^*(-A-B)$	$B+A-9^*((-8+7-6^*5)^*4^\wedge 3-2^*1)$
A434	17896	$1-2^*-3^*4^*567-89A^*B$	$-B-A98+7^*-654^*-3-21$
A435	17897	$1-2-(-34^*56-(7+89AB))$	$BA9+8765-43^*-21$
A436	17898	$12+34^*56-7+89AB$	$BA98+7^*6^*-54-3+21$
A437	17899	$1+2345-(6+7)-89A^*B$	$B+A9^*87+6^*543-21$
A438	17900	$1-2^*-3^*456+(-7-89A)^*B$	$-B+A987+6-543-(2+1)$
A439	17901	$-1^*-23^*(-4+567+8-9-AB)$	$-B+A987+6-543+2^*-1$
A43A	17902	$(-1+2^\wedge 2-3+4^*5)^*(-6-7)^*-8^*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987+6-543-2+1$
A43B	17903	$1-(-2+(-3+4-5^*6)/7)^8+9+A^*B$	$-B+A987+65^*-4-321$
A440	17904	$((1+2^*3+4)^\wedge 5+(-6-7)^*8)/9+A^*B$	$-B+A987-(-6+543-2)-1$
A441	17905	$((1+2)^\wedge 3+4^\wedge 5-(-6-7)^*(8+9)+A+B)$	$-B+A987+6+(543-2)^*-1$
A442	17906	$(1-2^\wedge 3)^\wedge 4+5^*6-7^*(8+9)+A^*B$	$-B+A987+6-(543-(2+1))$
A443	17907	$(-1-2^*3+4^\wedge (5+6-7))^*8^*9-(A+B)$	$B+A-98^*(-76-54)-3+21$
A444	17908	$1-234^*(-56+7+8)-9^*-AB$	$B^*(A98-7-65-4^*(-32-1))$
A445	17909	$1-23^*-4^*56-(7-89)^*-A^*-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7-6)^*(-5^*4-3^\wedge 2+1)$
A446	17910	$-1+2345+(-6+7)^*-89A^*B$	$B+A987-(6+543)-(2+1)$
A447	17911	$1+2345-(-6-(-7-89A^*-B))$	$B+A987-6-543+2^*-1$
A448	17912	$12+34^*56+7+89AB$	$B+A987-(6+543)-2+1$
A449	17913	$1+2345+6+7-89A^*B$	$B-(-A+9^*(-876-(543-21)))$
A44A	17914	$-12+3^*4^*(56-(7-8)+9AB)$	$-B+A987-6-543+2-1$
A44B	17915	$1^*-23+45^*67+89^*AB$	$B-A9-876-543^*-21$
A450	17916	$1+(-2-3^*-4^*5)^*6-7^*8^*9+A^*B$	$-B+A987-(6+543-21)$
A451	17917	$-12-34^*5^*(6-78+9)+AB$	$B-A-9^*-8^*-7-6^*5^*-432^*1$
A452	17918	$1-2^*3^*-4^*567-(89A^*B)$	$-B-A-9^*(8-(-7^*-6+5^*4)^3)+2/1$
A453	17919	$1+(-2^*-3)^\wedge 4^*(5/-6^*7+8)-9+A^*B$	$-B^*(A+9-(-87-65-4^*-321))$
A454	17920	$-12^*34^*(5-(6-(7-8))-(9-(-A-B)))$	$B+A987+65^*(-4-3-(2+1))$
A455	17921	$(1+2)^\wedge (3+4)+5^*6+7(8)^\wedge 9+A^*B$	$B-A^*9-8^*76^*(-54-(32-1))$
A456	17922	$(-1+2^\wedge 2-3+4^*5)^*(-6-7)^*-8^*9+A^*B$	$B-(-A987-6-(543-2-1))$
A457	17923	$-1+2345+6+7+89A^*B$	$B+A987+6+(543+2)^*-1$
A458	17924	$-123+4567+8^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A987+6-543-2+1$
A459	17925	$1+2345+6-(-7-89A^*B)$	$B+A987+65^*-4-321$
A45A	17926	$1-2+3^*4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9+A^*B$	$B-(-A987-6+543)+2-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A45B	17927	$(-1-2^3+4^4(5+6-7))^8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6+543)+2^*1$
A460	17928	$1^*23^*(-45^*6+789-AB)$	$-B+A987+6-543+21$
A461	17929	$1^*2+3^*4^5*6-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B^*-A+9^*(-8-7)^*(-6-5^*4^3)^*2-1$
A462	17930	$-12+3+4^*-5^*-678-9^*AB$	$B^*A^*(9+87-(-65+43)+21)$
A463	17931	$-12+3-45^*-67+89^*AB$	$B+A987+6-5^*43^*(2+1)$
A464	17932	$1+2+3^*4^5*6-7^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$-BA+9876+5-43^*-21$
A465	17933	$(-1+2-3^*-4^5)^*6-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4-(-3-2))-1$
A466	17934	$-1^*-2^*(-3-(-4567-89A)-B)$	$-B-A+9^*(8^*7+6^5/4-3-2)^{\wedge}1$
A467	17935	$(-1+(-2^3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5+6/7+8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9^*(-8-7^*-6)^*5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
A468	17936	$1^*-2-3-4^*5^*-678+9^*-AB$	$-B-A+(9+(8-7^*(6-5)+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
A469	17937	$1+(-2^*-3)^{\wedge}4^*(-5/-6^*7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7/6+5^{\wedge}4/(3-2^{\wedge}-1))$
A46A	17938	$-1-2^*(-3-4^*5)^*-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6-543+21$
A46B	17939	$1+23^*(4+5)^*67-(89A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7-6^5/4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1$
A470	17940	$1^*(23-4)^*(-56+78)^*(9-(-A-B))$	$BA98-7-(65^*(-4+32))-1$
A471	17941	$-1^*(-2-3^*4^5)^*6-7^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7+6^5/4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1$
A472	17942	$1^*23+45^*6^*7^*8+9A-B$	$B-A98+7^*-654^*-3-2+1$
A473	17943	$-12+3-4^*5+(6-78)^*(-9-A)^*B$	$-BA9+8^*(-7+6+54)^*(32+1)$
A474	17944	$((1/-2+3)/4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7-(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9+(8^*7^*6^{\wedge}(5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
A475	17945	$-12+3456+(-789A)^*-B$	$B-(A98+7^*-654^*3)-2^*-1$
A476	17946	$-1^*-2^*(3+4567+89A-B)$	$BA-98^*-76-5+4321$
A477	17947	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4^5)^*(6-(7+8+9))-(A-B)$	$B+A+9+(8^*7+6)^*(5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
A478	17948	$1+2+345^*(6-7-(-8-9)+A+B)$	$-B+A987+6^*-5^*4^*3^*-2^*-1$
A479	17949	$-12-3^*45^*(-6-7)^*8+9AB$	$BA98+7+6^*(-5^*-4-321)$
A47A	17950	$12345+6^*(-789-A)+B$	$B+A987-(-6+543)+21$
A47B	17951	$1^*2+3^*4^5*6-7^*8^*9+A+B$	$BA98+7^*-6^*54-3^*-21$
A480	17952	$-1+2345-6^*-7+89A^*B$	$BA98+7-65^*(-4+32)-1$
A481	17953	$-12-3^*-45^*(6-(7+8)-9+AB)$	$B-A^*-987+65^*43+21$
A482	17954	$1-(-2345+6^*-7)+89A^*B$	$B+A^*-9-876+543^*21$
A483	17955	$-123^*(-4+5)^*(-67+89-AB)$	$B+A-9^*(8-(-7^*-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)-(-2+1)$
A484	17956	$1+23^*(-4+5+67-8+9-AB)$	$BA-98^*-76+5+4321$
A485	17957	$-1+2345+(-6-78-9)^*-AB$	$BA-9^*(8-(-7^*-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)-(-2-1)$
A486	17958	$1^*2^*(345-(-678^*9+A^*B))$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4-(-3^*2-1))$
A487	17959	$1+(-2^*-3)^{\wedge}4^*(-5/-6^*7+8)+9+A+B$	$B+A-9-87^*(-6+54)^*-3+21$
A488	17960	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(8-(-7^*-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+2/1$
A489	17961	$1+(-2-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6))/7-8^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
A48A	17962	$12^*(34-(-5+6-789-AB))$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7)^*-6^*(-5^*-4+3)^*2+1$
A48B	17963	$-1-(-2+345+(-6-7)^*(-8+9AB))$	$-B-A98-765^*(4+3-21)$
A490	17964	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3+4)^*5^*(-6^*7^*8+9)-(A+B)$	$-B-A+(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
A491	17965	$1+(-2-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6))/7-8-9+A+B$	$-B-A-9+(-8+7+6)^*((-5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
A492	17966	$-1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4-5^*(-6+7^*8)^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3^*2)-1$
A493	17967	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4^5)^*(6-(7+8+9))+A+B$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7+6^5/4-3^*2)^{\wedge}1$
A494	17968	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3+4^5+6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA+98^*(76+54)-32^*1$
A495	17969	$(-1-2^*3^*(-4-5)^*6)^*7^*8-9-A^*B$	$-B-A^*(-987-6+54-321)$
A496	17970	$1^*-2^*(-34-56-7^*89A+B)$	$-B-A+9^*(8^*7+6^5/4-3+2)^{\wedge}1$
A497	17971	$1-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*-5^*(6-7^*(8+9))-A^*B$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3-2)+1$
A498	17972	$(-1-2^*(3-(4^5+6)^*-7^*8)^*9+A-B)$	$-B-A9+8^*(-7+6+5^*(-4+321))$
A499	17973	$12+3456+(-789A)^*-B$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4-3)^*2/1$
A49A	17974	$(1/-2+3)^*(4^5+6)^*7-8^*9+A+B$	$B^*(-A9+876+54+321)$
A49B	17975	$1+2^*(34+5678)-9A^*B$	$-B+A987+65^*(-4-3+2^*-1)$
A4A0	17976	$-1^*-2^*(3-4-5)^*(-67+8-9AB)$	$-B+A987-65-432-1$
A4A1	17977	$(-1-(2/3+4)-5^*6)^*-7^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$-BA+9^*(876+543)-2^*-1$
A4A2	17978	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4567-(-89A-B))$	$-B+A987-(-65+432-1)$
A4A3	17979	$-1-(-2^{\wedge}3-3^*-4^5+6)^*(-7-8)^*9-A^*B$	$-B-A+9^*(8+7-6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^*2/1$
A4A4	17980	$-1-(-2^*(-3+4^5+6)+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-(A9+8^*(-7+6)^*5^*(-4+321))$
A4A5	17981	$-1+2345-6+(-7-89A)^*-B$	$B+A+(9+8+(-7^*6+5+4)^{\wedge}3)/-2+1$
A4A6	17982	$-1+2+(-34-5^*-6^*7)^*89+AB$	$-B-A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4)+3^{\wedge}(2-1)$
A4A7	17983	$123-4+(-5-6-7)^*(8+9)^*-AB$	$BA-9+(-8-7+6-5)^*43^*-21$
A4A8	17984	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3+4)^*-5^*(-6^*7^*8+9)+A-B$	$-BA+9^*(876+543+2-1)$
A4A9	17985	$1^*(-2+345^*-6-(-7-89A))^*-B$	$-B^*(A9-(-87+6)-543)^*(2+1)$
A4AA	17986	$-123-45^*-67+89A^*B$	$B+A+9+(8+7^*6^{\wedge}(5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2^*1$
A4AB	17987	$-1-2^*(-3+456^*-7)^*(-8+9-(A-B))$	$-B-A+9^*-8+7^*6^5*4^*3-2^*1$
A4B0	17988	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3+4^5+6^*7)^*(8+9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A+9^*(8^*7+6^5/4+3-2)^{\wedge}1$
A4B1	17989	$-1+2345+67-89A^*-B$	$-B+A^*(98-76-5+43)^*21$
A4B2	17990	$1^*2345+67-89A^*-B$	$B+A+(9-8+(7^*6-5-4)^{\wedge}3)/2^{\wedge}1$
A4B3	17991	$123-45^*-6^*-7^*-8-(9-A)+B$	$B+A+(9-8+(7^*6-5-4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
A4B4	17992	$1^*2+34^*567-89A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3)-2/1$
A4B5	17993	$1+2-34^*-567-89A^*B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3)-(-2-1)$
A4B6	17994	$1^*-2^*-3^*(-4^*-5^*67-8+9AB)$	$B+A+9^*(8^*7+6^5/4-3/(2-1))$
A4B7	17995	$1+2345+6+(-7-89A)^*-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3)+2-1$
A4B8	17996	$1-2^*(3+4^*-5^*(-6+7^*8)^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B^*(A9+876-5^*(-43-2))^*1$
A4B9	17997	$-1^*2+(3^{\wedge}(4-5+6)+7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3)+2+1$
A4BA	17998	$12345-6^*789-(-A+B)$	$B+A987-65-432-1$
A4BB	17999	$12345-6^*-789^*(A-B)$	$B+A987-65+432^*-1$
A500	18000	$-1^*-2^*-34^*(-5-6-78-(-9+AB))$	$B-(-A987+65+432)+1$
A501	18001	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8-7)-6-5)^*((-4^*-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
A502	18002	$1-2^*((-3-4^*5^{\wedge}6)/7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8-(-7^*-6^*5+21))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
A503	18003	$(-1-2)^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6-7^*8^*9+A+B$	$-B-(A+9)-(-876-543^*21)$
A504	18004	$12-34^*-567-89A^*B$	$B+A-9-(8-7^*(6^5-4^{\wedge}3))/(2+1)$
A505	18005	$12345-6^*(789+A-B)$	$-B-A98-7^*-6^*(5+4+321)$
A506	18006	$-1-2-3^*(-4-567^*8)-9^*AB$	$B+A+(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
A507	18007	$-1^*-2^*(3-4^*-5^*(-6+7^*8)^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B-A-9+(-8+7+6)^*((-5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
A508	18008	$1+2-34^*5^*-67+89^*(A+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-(6^5/4+3))^*2+1$
A509	18009	$-1^*-23^*(456+7+8+9+A+B)$	$-B-A-9+((-9^*(-8^*-7^*-6+5)+4)^*-3^*2-1)$
A50A	18010	$(1+(2-3^*4)^{\wedge}5/(6-7^*8))^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A987^*(6+5)^*-4^*(-3-2+1)$
A50B	18011	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(-6^*7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B-A^*987-(6+54)^*-321$
A510	18012	$(-1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5+6+7+8))^*9+A+B$	$BA-987-6+543^*21$
A511	18013	$-123+4+5-678^*(-9-A)+B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4+3-2)+1$
A512	18014	$-1-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*(5-(-6-7^*8)^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A^*-98-76-543^*-21$
A513	18015	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4)^*3^*2/1$
A514	18016	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-(-7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7-6^5/4)+3^*-2+1$
A515	18017	$(1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-((-9-8)^*(7-(-6^*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))))-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A516	18018	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (-4 \cdot 5^6 - 67 + 8 + 9 + A + B)$	$-B \cdot (-A - 9 + 87 - 6) \cdot (5 - 43 + 21)$
A517	18019	$12345 + 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8^9 \cdot (9 - A^* - B)$	$B + A - 9^* \cdot (-8^* 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 + 3^{\wedge} 2) - 1$
A518	18020	$12345 - 6^* 789 + A + B$	$B + A + 9^* (8 + 7 - 6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 2 - 1$
A519	18021	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 - 7 - 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A987 + 6 + (5 + 4)^* 3^* 2 - 1$
A51A	18022	$-1 - 2^* \cdot 3^* \cdot (-4 \cdot 5^6 - 6^* \cdot 7^* 8^* 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9^* (8 + 7 - 6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 2 + 1$
A51B	18023	$(1 / (-2 + 3))^* (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6)^* 7 + 8 - 9 + A - B$	$-B + A987 + 6^* - 5 - 432 - 1$
A520	18024	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 + (7 - 8)^{\wedge} 9 + A - B$	$-B + A987 + 6^* - 5 + 432^* - 1$
A521	18025	$-1 + 234^* (56 - 7 - 8) - 9A^* - B$	$-B + A - 987 + (-6 - 543)^* \cdot 21$
A522	18026	$-12 + 34^* (5 - 67 + 89 + A) \cdot B$	$B + A - 9^* (-8^* 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4) + 3 + 2^{\wedge} 1$
A523	18027	$1 - 23^* (-4 - 5)^* 6 + 7 + 8 - 9^* A B$	$B - A - 987 - (-6 - 543)^* 21$
A524	18028	$1^* 2 - 3^* (-4^{\wedge} 5^6 - (-7 - 8)^* 9) + A - B$	$B + A - 9^* (-8^* 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4) - 3^* - 2 + 1$
A525	18029	$1^{\wedge} 2 - 3^* (-4^{\wedge} 5^6 - (-7 - 8)^* 9) - (A - B)$	$-BA - 9^* (-8 - 76 + 543)^* (-2 - 1)$
A526	18030	$(1 + (2 - 3^* 4)^{\wedge} 5 / (6 - 7^* 8))^* 9 + A + B$	$BA987 + 6 - 5^* (-4 + 32 - 1)$
A527	18031	$1 + 2 + 34^* 5^* - 6 + 78^* (9 + A) \cdot B$	$B + A - 9^* (-8^* 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4) + 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
A528	18032	$-12^* (3 - 4)^* (5 - 6)^* (-7 - 89A - B)$	$B + A - (9 + (8 - 7^* 6)^* ((5^* 4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1))$
A529	18033	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9^* - 8 + 7)^* \cdot 6^* (-5^* (4 + 3) - (2 + 1))$
A52A	18034	$-1 + 2 - 3 - 4 - (56 - 7 + 89)^* A^* - B$	$BA + 9^* (876 + 543 - 21)$
A52B	18035	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B - A9 + 8^* (-765 - 43)^* - 2 - 1$
A530	18036	$1^* 23^* 4^* (-5 - (-67 + 8 - 9^* A) + B)$	$-B - A - 9^* (-8 + 7^* 6)^* (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) + 2 + 1$
A531	18037	$1 + (-2 - 3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^* 7)^* (8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B^* - A + 9 + (8^* 7 + 6)^* (5 + 4^* 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
A532	18038	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge} 3 - 4^* (-5 / -6 + 7)^* 8)^* 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - 9^* ((-8^* 7 + 6)^* (5 - 4 / -3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
A533	18039	$-1 + 2^* (3 + 4567 + 8 - 9A^* - B)$	$-B^* - A + 9 - 8 - 7^* (-6^{\wedge} 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3)^* - 2^* 1$
A534	18040	$1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (-3 - 4567 - 8 - 9A^* B)$	$-BA^* (-9 + 8)^* (-7 - (-6 - 5))^* (4 + 32 - 1)$
A535	18041	$12 - (3 - 456 + 78^* 9^* (-A - B))$	$BA98 - 76 - (54^* 32 + 1)$
A536	18042	$(-1 - 2^* (3 - 4^{\wedge} 5) - 6^* 7 + 8)^* 9 - (A + B)$	$BA98 - 76 - 54^* 32^* 1$
A537	18043	$(1 / (-2 + 3))^* (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6)^* 7 + 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$B - A + 9 - 876 + 543^* 21$
A538	18044	$-1 - 2^* \cdot 3^* \cdot (-4 \cdot 5^6 - 6^* \cdot 7^* 8^* 9) + A + B$	$-B + A987 - (6 + 5 + 432 - 1)$
A539	18045	$(1 / (-2 + 3))^* (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6)^* 7 + 8 - 9 + A + B$	$B + A - 9 - 876 - 543^* 21$
A53A	18046	$1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (-3 - 4)^* (56 - (-789 - A^* B))$	$-B - A9^* - 8 - (76 - 543)^* 21$
A53B	18047	$-1 + 23^* 456 + 7^* 89 - A - B$	$B + A987 - 6^* 5 - (432 - 1)$
A540	18048	$12345 + 6^* (-789 + A) - B$	$B + A + 9^* (8^* 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 + 3 / (2 - 1))$
A541	18049	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - (9^* - 876 - 54^* 321)$
A542	18050	$-1^* (2 - 34)^* (-5 - 6^* (-78 - (9 - A) + B))$	$B + A - 9^* (-8^* 7 - (6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 + 3)) + 2^* 1$
A543	18051	$1 - 2 - 3^* - 4 - (-56 + 7 - 89)^* A^* B$	$-B^* (-A98 - (76 - 5)) - (4 - 3) - (-2 + 1)$
A544	18052	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 + 7^* 8 - 9 - (A + B)$	$BA - 9 + 87^* (-6 + 54)^* 3 - 2 - 1$
A545	18053	$1 + 23^* 456 - 78^* 9 + A^* - B$	$-B - (A - 9876 - 5) - 43^* - 21$
A546	18054	$1 - 2^* (-3 - 4^* \cdot 5^* (6 - 7^* 8))^* 9 + A - B$	$-B + A987 - 6 + 5 - (432 - 1)$
A547	18055	$1^* (-23 + 4)^* \cdot 5^* \cdot (-67 + 89 + AB)$	$BA98 - 7 - 6 - 54^* (32 + 1)$
A548	18056	$1 - 2 - 3 - (45 + 67 + 8)^* (-9A - B)$	$-B + A987 + 6 - 5 - 432 + 1$
A549	18057	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 + A + B$	$BA9 + 8^* (76 - 543)^* (-2 - 1)$
A54A	18058	$(-1 - 2^* 3^* (-4 - 5)^* 6)^* 7^* 8 - 9 - (A + B)$	$B + A + (9 + 8)^* (7^* 6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge} (3 + 2^{\wedge} 1))$
A54B	18059	$-1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (3 - (-4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + 7 + 8)^* 9) + A - B$	$B + A - ((-9 - 8)^* (7 - (-6^* 5 - 4^{\wedge} (3 + 2)))) - 1$
A550	18060	$-1^* (-2 + 3 - (-45 + 6 - 78))^* (-9A - B)$	$-BA + 9876 + 54^* (-3 + 21)$
A551	18061	$-1 + 234^* (56 - 7) + 8 + 9A^* - B$	$B + A - (9^* - 8^* (7 - 6^* 5) - 4^{\wedge} (3^* 2 + 1))$
A552	18062	$-12 + 3 + 45^* (-67 - 8 + 9A)^* B$	$-B + A987 - 6^* (54 + 32 - 1)$
A553	18063	$1^* 23^* (-4 + 567 - 89 - A - B)$	$-B - (-A - (9876 - 5)) - 43^* - 21$
A554	18064	$12345 + 6 + 7^* 8^* - 9A - B$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 - (432 + 1)$
A555	18065	$1 - 2 - (3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 - 9 - A^* B$	$-B - (-A987 - 6) + 5 + 432^* - 1$
A556	18066	$-12 - 34 - 5^* - 6^* (-7^* - 89 - AB)$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 - 432 + 1$
A557	18067	$-1 - 23 + 4567 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$B + A - 9^* (-8^* 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 - 3 - 2) + 1$
A558	18068	$1^* - 23 + 4567 - 8^* 9A^* - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8^* (-7 - 6^* 5)^* (4^{\wedge} 3 - (2 + 1))$
A559	18069	$1 - 23 + 4567 + 8^* 9A^* B$	$-B - (-A - 9^* - 876 + 54^* - 321)$
A55A	18070	$(-1 + 2)^* (-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^* 7)^* (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A + (-9^* - 8 - 7^* - 6^* 5) / 4^{\wedge} - 3 + 2 - 1$
A55B	18071	$1 - 23^* - 456 - 7^* - 89 - A + B$	$B - A + 9^* - 876 + 54^* 321$
A560	18072	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 + 7^* 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 - 6^* (54 + 32 + 1)$
A561	18073	$1 + 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^* 7)^* (8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B + A + 9876 + 5 - 43^* - 21$
A562	18074	$12^* (34 - (-5 + 6 + 7 - (89A - B)))$	$B - (-A987 + 6 - 5) - 432 - 1$
A563	18075	$1^* (2 + 3)^* (-4^* (-567 - 89) - (-A + B))$	$B + A987 - 6 - (-5 + 432^* 1)$
A564	18076	$1 - 2^* (-3 - 4^* \cdot 5^* (6 - 7^* 8))^* 9 + A + B$	$B - (-A987 + 6) - (-5 + 432 - 1)$
A565	18077	$-1 - 2^{\wedge} 3^* (4 - 5^* (-6 + 7^* 8)^* 9) + A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 - 5 + 432^* - 1$
A566	18078	$1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot 3^* (-4 - 5 - (6 + 7) + 8 - 9)^* \cdot AB$	$B + A - 9^* (-8 + 7^* 6)^* (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) + 2 + 1$
A567	18079	$(1^{\wedge} - 2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4^* \cdot 5^* (-6 - (-7 / 8 + 9)) + A - B$	$-B - A^* 9^* (-8 - (76 - (-54 - 32) + 1))$
A568	18080	$-12 - 3^* 45^* - 6^* 7 + 8^* 9AB$	$BA - 9 + 87^* (-6 + 54)^* 3 + 21$
A569	18081	$-1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot (3 - (-4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + 7 + 8)^* 9) + A + B$	$BA98 + 7 + 6 - 54^* (32 + 1)$
A56A	18082	$-12 + 3^* 4^* (56 + 7 + 8 + 9AB)$	$B - A9 - (87 - (-6 + 5))^* (4 + 3)^* - 21$
A56B	18083	$1 - 2 + 3^* 4^* (-5 - 6)^* (-7 - 8 + 9 - AB)$	$-B + A987 - 6^* - 5 - 432 - 1$
A570	18084	$-12 + 3 + 4567 + 8^* - 9A^* - B$	$-B^* (A9 + 8^* 7 - (6 - 5) - 4^* 321)$
A571	18085	$1^{\wedge} 2 - (3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 + 9 - A^* B$	$B + A + 9876 - 5 + 43^* 21$
A572	18086	$123 - 45^* - 6^* - 7^* - 8 + 9A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 + 5 - 432 - 1$
A573	18087	$((1 + 2)^{\wedge} 3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 + 7)^* (8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 + 5 + 432^* - 1$
A574	18088	$1^* (-2 + 34)^* (5 - (678 - 9AB))$	$B - (-A987 - 6 - 5 + 432 - 1)$
A575	18089	$-1 - 2 - 3 + 4567 - 8^* 9A^* - B$	$B + A - 9^* 8 + (-7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 + 4^* 3) / (-2 - 1)$
A576	18090	$1^* (-2 + 3)^* (4 + 5 + 6)^* (-78 - 9A^* - B)$	$-B - A - 9 + (8 - 7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 + 4^{\wedge} 3) / (-2 - 1)$
A577	18091	$-1^* \cdot 2^* \cdot 3^* (-4 + 5 - 6^* 7^* 8)^* 9 - (A - B)$	$-B + A + 9^* (876 + 543) - 21$
A578	18092	$(1 + 2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5^{\wedge} 6 - 7 + 8^* 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A - 9^* 8 + 7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 / (4 - (3 - 2)) - 1$
A579	18093	$-1 + 2 + (-3 + 4^{\wedge} 5 + 6^* 7)^* (8 + 9) + A + B$	$B + A - 9^* 8 + 7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 / (4 - 3 + 2^{\wedge} 1)$
A57A	18094	$-1^* 2^* (-345 - 6^* (7 - 8))^* \cdot 9AB$	$B + A + 9 + 8^* 7^* 6^* 5 + 4^{\wedge} (3^* 2 + 1)$
A57B	18095	$1^* (234 + 5 + 6^* 7 + 89A)^* B$	$B - (-A - 9876) - (-5 + 43^* - 21)$
A580	18096	$(1 / (-2 + 3))^* (4^{\wedge} 5 + 6)^* 7 + 8^* 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9^* (-8 - 7) - 6 / 5 - 4^* 3)^* (-3 - 2) / 1$
A581	18097	$1 - 2 - (-3 - 4567) - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B + A - 9^* 8 + (-7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 - 4^* 3) / (-2 - 1)$
A582	18098	$((1^{\wedge} 2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4 - 5 / -6 - 7)^* 8^* 9 + A^* B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2 - 1$
A583	18099	$(-1 - 2^* - 3^* (-4 - 5)^* 6)^* - 7^* 8 + 9 - A^* B$	$-B + A - 9^* (-876 - 543 + 2) + 1$
A584	18100	$1^* 2 + 3 + 4567 - 8^* 9A^* - B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2 + 1$
A585	18101	$1 + 2 + 3 + 4567 - 8^* - 9A^* B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 / (2 - 1)$
A586	18102	$-1 - 23 + 4^* \cdot 5^* \cdot 678 + 9^* - A^* B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 + 2 - 1$
A587	18103	$1 - ((-2 - 3^{\wedge} 4)^* (-5^* - 6^* 7 + 8) - 9) + A - B$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 + 2^{\wedge} 1$
A588	18104	$1234 + 56^* (7 + 89 + AB)$	$B + A + 9^* 8^* 7 + (6 + 5^* 4)^{\wedge} 3 + 2 + 1$
A589	18105	$-12 - 3 - 45 - (-678^* (9 + A) - B)$	$-B - A - 9 - 8 + 7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 / (4 - 3 + 2) - 1$
A58A	18106	$1234 + 567 + 89AB$	$BA98 - 76 - 54^* (32 - 1)$
A58B	18107	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge} 3)^* - 4^* (5 - 6 - 7^* - 8^* 9) + A - B$	$-BA + 9 + 8^* (-76 - 5)^* 4^* 3^* 2^* - 1$
A590	18108	$1^* 2^* (-3 + 45 + 678)^* - 9^* (A - B)$	$-B - A + 9 + (8 - 7^* 6^{\wedge} 5 + 4^{\wedge} 3) / (-2 - 1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A591	18109	$12345 \cdot 6 \cdot 789 \cdot A \cdot B$	$B+A+(9 \cdot 8-7 \wedge 6+5)/(-4-3/2-1)$
A592	18110	$12 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (-56 \cdot 7-8 \cdot 9AB)$	$B+A-9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6+5-4) \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 1$
A593	18111	$1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (-5+67+8+9AB)$	$-BA9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot (-5-43-2 \cdot 1)$
A594	18112	$12+3 \cdot (-4567+8 \cdot 9A \cdot B)$	$B+A-9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6+5-4) \cdot 3 \cdot 2+1$
A595	18113	$(-1-2 \wedge 3) \cdot 4 \cdot (-5/6-7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9)+A \cdot B$	$B-A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot (-6-(-5+43) \cdot (2+1))$
A596	18114	$-1 \cdot (2 \wedge 3+(-4 \wedge 5-6 \cdot 7) \cdot (8+9)) \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$-B+A987+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 \cdot (3+2)$
A597	18115	$(1-2 \cdot 3) \wedge 4 \cdot (-5+6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$-B-A-9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5/4/3/2+1$
A598	18116	$12 \cdot (3-45+67 \cdot (8+9) \cdot A+B)$	$-B+A987 \cdot 6 \cdot (54+3+2)$
A599	18117	$1 \cdot -23 \cdot (-456-7 \cdot (-8-(-9 \cdot A \cdot B)))$	$B \cdot (A+9+8) \cdot (-7+65-4-3 \cdot 2+1)$
A59A	18118	$1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6-7 \cdot (-89 \cdot A)) \cdot B$	$BA98-7 \cdot 6 \cdot (54 \cdot 32+1)$
A59B	18119	$(-1-2 \wedge 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5/6-7)) \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$BA98-7 \cdot 6+54 \cdot 32 \cdot -1$
A5A0	18120	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot (3-45+678) \cdot (-9+A \cdot B)$	$B-A-9 \cdot (-876-543) \cdot 2 \cdot -1$
A5A1	18121	$1+2 \cdot 3+5 \cdot 678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A) \cdot B$	$-B-A+9 \cdot (876+543)+21$
A5A2	18122	$1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4 \wedge 5/6+7) \cdot (8+9)+A \cdot B$	$-B-A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7/6 \wedge (5-4-3) \cdot 2+1$
A5A3	18123	$1+23+4567+8 \cdot 9A \cdot B$	$-B-A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot (-5-4+3 \cdot (2-1))$
A5A4	18124	$1 \cdot (2+3) \wedge 4 \cdot (-5 \cdot 6+(-7-8) \wedge 9)+A \cdot B$	$-B-A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \wedge (6-5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \wedge 2+1$
A5A5	18125	$1-234+5 \cdot (6+7) \cdot (8-9AB)$	$-BA \cdot (98+7) \cdot 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (-432+1)$
A5A6	18126	$-1-2+3 \cdot 45 \cdot (678-9A \cdot B)$	$B+A987 \cdot (65 \cdot (4+3)+21)$
A5A7	18127	$-1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot (45 \cdot 678 \cdot (9+A)) \cdot B$	$-B-A+(-9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4)/3+2+1$
A5A8	18128	$1 \cdot (23+4)+5 \cdot (678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A)+B)$	$B \cdot (-A+98-7 \cdot 6+5 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2+1)$
A5A9	18129	$-1-23 \cdot 45 \cdot 67+89A \cdot B$	$B+A+9 \cdot (876-(-543+2 \cdot 1))$
A5AA	18130	$12345+6 \cdot 789+AB$	$-B+A987-65 \cdot 4 \cdot 321$
A5AB	18131	$1-23+45 \cdot 67 \cdot 89A \cdot B$	$BA98-7+6+54 \cdot 32 \cdot 1$
A5B0	18132	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4+567-(-8+9)) \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$-B+A987+65-432+1$
A5B1	18133	$(1-2 \cdot 3) \wedge 4 \cdot (-5+6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$BA98+7 \cdot 6+54 \cdot 32 \cdot -1$
A5B2	18134	$(1+2+3) \wedge 4 \cdot (5-6+7+8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$BA98-(-7+6+54 \cdot 32 \cdot -1)$
A5B3	18135	$1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4-5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B+A+(-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6+5) \cdot -4 \cdot -3/2 \cdot 1$
A5B4	18136	$-1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (4 \cdot (-5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9)) \cdot A \cdot B$	$-BA-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (432-1)$
A5B5	18137	$-12-3 \cdot 4+5 \cdot 678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A) \cdot B$	$B-A+9 \cdot (876+543+2)+1$
A5B6	18138	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34+5+6 \cdot (-78-9AB))$	$-B+A987-65+4 \cdot 321$
A5B7	18139	$1+(-2+3+4+5+6 \cdot 7) \cdot (8+9)+A \cdot B$	$B \cdot (-A+98+7 \cdot (-6-5+4) \cdot 3 \cdot 2+1)$
A5B8	18140	$-12-3+45 \cdot 67 \cdot 89A \cdot B$	$B+A+(-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5)/(-4-3+2) \cdot -1$
A5B9	18141	$-1 \cdot (2+(-3+4+5)) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot A \cdot B$	$-B+A987-6 \cdot 54 \cdot 321$
A5BA	18142	$-1+2/3 \wedge (4-5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B+A+(-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5)/(-4-3+2)+1$
A5BB	18143	$1 \cdot 2/3 \wedge (4-5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B-A-9 \cdot (876+543) \cdot 2+1$
A600	18144	$12-34-5 \cdot 678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A)+B$	$BA98+7+6 \cdot 54 \cdot 32 \cdot -1$
A601	18145	$-12-3 \cdot (-4-5+678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A)+B)$	$B-A-9 \cdot (-876-(-543+2+1))$
A602	18146	$-12+3 \cdot 45 \cdot 67 \cdot 89A \cdot B$	$BA98+7+6+54 \cdot 32+1$
A603	18147	$-1 \cdot -2+(-3-(-4-5)) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$-B-A9-87+6 \cdot 5 \cdot (-432+1)$
A604	18148	$1+2+(-3+4+5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$B+A-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5/(-4+3-2/1)$
A605	18149	$-1 \cdot -2 \cdot 3 \cdot (4 \cdot (-5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9)) \cdot A \cdot B$	$-B-A987-6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4321$
A606	18150	$1+23-45+678 \cdot (9+A)+B$	$-B \cdot (-A98-(-7+6+5+43+21))$
A607	18151	$-1-2+345 \cdot 6 \cdot 7+89AB$	$-B+A9-876+543 \cdot 21$
A608	18152	$(-1-2 \cdot 3) \cdot (-4-5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B \cdot (-A987+65) \cdot (-4+321)$
A609	18153	$1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4-5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B \cdot (-A987-65)+432 \cdot -1$
A60A	18154	$-12-345 \cdot 6+7+89AB$	$B+A987+65-432+1$
A60B	18155	$-1+2+345 \cdot 6 \cdot 7+89AB$	$-BA-98 \cdot (-7+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432 \cdot -1)$
A610	18156	$-1-2 \cdot (-345-678 \cdot 9) \cdot (-A+B)$	$-BA-98 \cdot 7+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432+1$
A611	18157	$1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 45 \cdot 67+89A \cdot B$	$B+A-9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5/4/3/2+1$
A612	18158	$-1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (4 \cdot (-5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9)) \cdot A+B$	$-B+A9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6+54321$
A613	18159	$-12-34 \cdot 5 \cdot (-6-78) \cdot 9AB$	$B+A+(-9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4))/3+2-1$
A614	18160	$-1+2 \cdot 345+67 \cdot (89+AB)$	$B+A987 \cdot (65 \cdot (-4-321))$
A615	18161	$-1 \cdot (-2+345-67 \cdot (89+AB))$	$-B \cdot (-A987-6+5 \cdot 4321)$
A616	18162	$1+2 \cdot 345+67 \cdot (89+AB)$	$B+A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge (5-4-3) \cdot 2-1$
A617	18163	$(-1 \cdot -2+(-3+4+5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9 \cdot (-A \cdot B)$	$B+A987-6 \cdot 54 \cdot 321$
A618	18164	$1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 45 \cdot 67+89A \cdot B$	$B+A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge (5-4-3) \cdot 2+1$
A619	18165	$-1-2 \cdot (-345 \cdot 6-7-89AB)$	$B+A+9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \wedge (6-5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \wedge 2 \cdot 1$
A61A	18166	$-1 \cdot (2+345 \cdot 6 \cdot (-7+89AB))$	$-BA-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432 \cdot -1$
A61B	18167	$1-2 \cdot (-345 \cdot 6-7)+89AB$	$-BA-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432+1$
A620	18168	$-1-2 \cdot 34 \cdot (-56-7)+89AB$	$BA-987 \cdot (-6-543) \cdot 21$
A621	18169	$-1+2 \cdot (-345 \cdot 6-7-89AB)$	$-BA-98+7+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432 \cdot 1$
A622	18170	$-1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7+8) \cdot 9A \cdot B$	$B+A+(9+8+7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4)/3-2 \wedge 1$
A623	18171	$1 \cdot -23 \cdot (-4 \cdot (-567-8)-9+AB)$	$B-A987-6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4321$
A624	18172	$12 \cdot (-3 \cdot (-45 \cdot 6 \cdot 7) \cdot (-8+9A \cdot B))$	$B \cdot (A98 \cdot (-76 \cdot 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 3) \cdot (2-1)$
A625	18173	$12-345-67 \cdot (-89-AB)$	$B+A9-876+543 \cdot 21$
A626	18174	$1+2+34 \cdot (56+7)+89AB$	$B+A+9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5/4/3/2 \cdot 1$
A627	18175	$1 \wedge 2 \cdot (-3-4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8-9+A \cdot B$	$B+A987+6 \cdot (-54+321)$
A628	18176	$1 \wedge 2 \cdot (3+4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8-9+A \cdot B$	$BA \cdot (98-76+54 \cdot 32 \cdot -1)$
A629	18177	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3+4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8-9+A \cdot B$	$-B-A9-87-6 \cdot 5 \cdot 432 \cdot -1$
A62A	18178	$-1 \cdot (-2-3-4+56+78) \cdot (9-AB)$	$B+A+9+8+(-7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4 \cdot 3)/(-2-1)$
A62B	18179	$-1/-2 \cdot ((3-(-4-5)) \wedge 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$-BA-98 \cdot (-76-54)+321$
A630	18180	$-1+23 \cdot (4-5)+678 \cdot (9+A) \cdot B$	$B-A9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6+54321$
A631	18181	$(-1+2) \cdot (-3+4 \wedge 5+6 \cdot 7) \cdot (8+9)+A \cdot B$	$B+A+9+8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5/(-4 \cdot (-3-2)) \cdot -1$
A632	18182	$1+2+3 \cdot (4-5) \cdot (-678 \cdot (9+A) \cdot B)$	$-B+A987+6 \cdot (-5-43-21)$
A633	18183	$-1 \cdot (23 \cdot (-45-6+7)+8) \cdot (9+A) \cdot B$	$B-A987+6 \cdot 5 \cdot 4321$
A634	18184	$1+2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4-5) \cdot (678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A) \cdot B)$	$BA+9-876-543 \cdot -21$
A635	18185	$1+23-45 \cdot 67+89A \cdot B$	$-B+A987+6 \cdot 5+4 \cdot 321$
A636	18186	$(1 \cdot (2+3) \wedge 4) \cdot (-5 \cdot 6+7/8) \cdot 9+A+B$	$B+A+(9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5 \cdot 4 \wedge 3)/(-2-1)$
A637	18187	$12 \cdot (3+4) \cdot (-5+678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A) \cdot B)$	$BA98-7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (5+43) \cdot -21$
A638	18188	$(-1 \cdot -2 \cdot (-3+4 \wedge 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B+A+(-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5)/(-4+3-2) \cdot -1$
A639	18189	$-12-3+45+678 \cdot (9+A) \cdot B$	$B+A+9+8+7+6 \wedge 5 \cdot (4+3)/(2+1)$
A63A	18190	$1 \cdot (-234 \cdot (-56-78)) \cdot (-9A+B)$	$B+A+9+(-8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 \wedge (5-4+3)) \cdot -2 \wedge 1$
A63B	18191	$-12-34 \cdot 5 \cdot 67+89 \cdot AB$	$B+A+9 \cdot (-8 \cdot 7/6 \wedge (-5+4-3)) \cdot 2+1$
A640	18192	$1-2 \cdot (3+4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8+9+A \cdot B$	$B+A+(9+8+7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4 \wedge 3)/(2+1)$
A641	18193	$12+345+6 \cdot (789+A) \cdot B$	$-BA \cdot (-9876+543 \cdot 2+1)$
A642	18194	$1+23-4 \cdot 5 \cdot 678 \cdot (-9 \cdot A)+B$	$-B \cdot (A98+7+65 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) \cdot -1$
A643	18195	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3+4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8+9+A \cdot B$	$B+A98 \cdot 7 \cdot 65+4321$
A644	18196	$1+2 \cdot (3+4) \wedge 5+6 \wedge 7/8+9+A \cdot B$	$-B \cdot (-A987+6+5 \cdot (-4-321))$
A645	18197	$-12-34 \cdot 5 \cdot (6-7)+89AB$	$-B \cdot (-A987+654-321)$
A646	18198	$1-2 \cdot 3 \cdot (-4+5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9+A \cdot B$	$B+A+9+(8+7 \cdot 6 \wedge 5+4 \wedge 3)/(2+1)$
A647	18199	$-1+23 \cdot 456+7 \cdot 89+AB$	$BA98-7+6 \cdot (54-321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A648	18200	$-12*(3+45+67-(8+9AB))$	$B-A9-8-7*-65*(4-32)*-1$
A649	18201	$123+456+78*-9*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7-6*-5*(-4-3*21)$
A64A	18202	$-1*2*(-345+6)*(-7-89+AB)$	$B+A*(-9*-8*-7+6^5)*(4-3/2)+1$
A64B	18203	$(-1+2)*-3*-4^5*6-7*(8+9)-A*B$	$-B-A+9*(8^7+6-5*4+3)^2-1$
A650	18204	$1-2+34*567+89*-AB$	$BA98-765-43*21$
A651	18205	$(-1-2*(3-4^5)+6)/(7-8))*9-A*B$	$-B+A987-6+(-5+4)*321$
A652	18206	$-1+2-34*-567+89*-AB$	$-B-(-A987+6-5+4+321)$
A653	18207	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6+7+8*9)+A+B$	$B+A987+6*-5-(-4+321)$
A654	18208	$1+2-(-34*567-89*-AB)$	$-B-(-A987-6)-(-5+4)-321$
A655	18209	$-1*(2+34-(-5+6+7)+89)*-AB$	$-B+A987+6*-5-4-3*21$
A656	18210	$(-1-2*-3*(-4-5)*6)*-7*8+9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9+8+7*(6^5+4*3)/(2+1)$
A657	18211	$(-1+2+3+4^5+6*7)*(8+9)+A+B$	$B+A*(-98+76)*(-54-3-2-1)$
A658	18212	$-1-2-(3+4)^5+6^7/8+9+A+B$	$BA+9*-876-54*-321$
A659	18213	$-1*2-(-3+4^5(5+6-7))*-8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6*(-5+4+321)$
A65A	18214	$12*(345+678-9-AB)$	$-BA+9-87+6*5*(432+1)$
A65B	18215	$(-1-2*3*-4*-5*(6+7))*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9876+(-5-43)*-21$
A660	18216	$1*2*(34+567+8-9-A)*B$	$-B+A987+6-5+4-321$
A661	18217	$1*2-(-3+4^5(5+6-7))*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6+(-5+4)*321$
A662	18218	$1+2-(-3+4^5(5+6-7))*-8*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6-(-5-4))-321$
A663	18219	$12-34*-567+89*-AB$	$B+A987-654+321$
A664	18220	$1-2*-3*(-4+5-6*-7*8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9*-8*-7*-6+5+4)*3*2+1$
A665	18221	$(-1+(-2*-3)^4+5)*(6+7-(8-9))+A+B$	$BA98+76+54*-32-1$
A666	18222	$-1+(-2*-3+4^5+6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-BA-98-7*6*5*-4*(3-21)$
A667	18223	$-1*(-2*-3+4^5+6*7)*(-8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+76-54*32+1$
A668	18224	$((1-2^3)^4+(-5-6*7)*8)*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8-7*(-65+4)*(32+1)$
A669	18225	$-1*23*(-456-7+89-AB)$	$-B+A987-6-5*-4-321$
A66A	18226	$1234-5*-6*-7*(8-(-9+A))*-B$	$-B+A987+6+5+4-321$
A66B	18227	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B*(-A98-76+54-3*21)$
A670	18228	$-12*-3*(456-(-7+89)+A*-B)$	$B-(-A987+6)-(-5+4)-321$
A671	18229	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^5*6+7)-8*9+A*B$	$B+A987*(6-5)-4-321$
A672	18230	$-1/(-2*-3)*((-4-5^6)*7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-5-4-321$
A673	18231	$1*2-3*(-4^5*6+7)-8*9-A*B$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4-3*2^1$
A674	18232	$-1+2*(-3+4^5-(-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4-3-2*1$
A675	18233	$1-2*(34+56)*(-7+8*-9-A-B)$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4-3-2+1$
A676	18234	$-1*2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9*(876+543)-21$
A677	18235	$1-2-3*(-4^5*6-(7-8*9))+A-B$	$-B-A9-8-7-6*-5*(432-1)$
A678	18236	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6-5)+4-321$
A679	18237	$-1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*5-4-321$
A67A	18238	$1-2+3+45+(67+8)*(-9-A)*-B$	$B+A987-(-6+5)-(-4+321)$
A67B	18239	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4+3-2+1$
A680	18240	$(-1+2^3+4^5+6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6+5-4-321$
A681	18241	$-1+(-2*(-3-4^5+6)-(7+8))*9+A-B$	$BA+9*(876+543-2)*1$
A682	18242	$-12*(3+4-56-789-AB)$	$-B+A987-6*(-5+43+21)$
A683	18243	$-1-2-3-456*-7+89*AB$	$B+A+9*(8^7+6-5^4)*3-2-1$
A684	18244	$-1-(2-3-4)^5*6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+7+6^5*(4+3)/(2+1)$
A685	18245	$(1*2+3)^4*5*6-7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8^7+6-5*4+3)^2-1$
A686	18246	$1-(2-3-4)^5*6-7*8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*-5+4+32*-1$
A687	18247	$1-2*(345+6)+78*(-9-A)*-B$	$B+A+9*(8^7+6-5*4+3)^2+1$
A688	18248	$1*2*(3+45*-6-(-7-8*-9*AB))$	$B-(-A987-6-5)+4-321$
A689	18249	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A9-8+7+6*5*(432-1)$
A68A	18250	$-1*(2-3+456*-7-89*AB)$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4-3-2^1$
A68B	18251	$(1/-2+3-4^5(5+6-7))*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4-3-2+1$
A690	18252	$12+3*(4+56*78)-(-9-(-A+B))$	$B+A+9+8+7*(-6*(5+4)+3)^2+1$
A691	18253	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7+8+9)-A*B$	$-BA-(9-(-8-7))+6*-5*-432-1$
A692	18254	$1*-2*(3-456+78-9AB)$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6/5^4-3+2^1$
A693	18255	$-1*2*(3+4^5-(-6+7)*8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+9*(8^7+6-5*4+3)^2+1$
A694	18256	$-12*(3-(-45+67)-(-89A+B))$	$BA9-8*(-765+43)*2-1$
A695	18257	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8)-9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4+3-2+1$
A696	18258	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A+B$	$BA98-7+6-5*(4+321)$
A697	18259	$-1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A+B$	$-B-A9-8-7-6*(-5*432+1)$
A698	18260	$12-3+456*7-89*-AB$	$BA98-(-7+6)+5*(-4-321)$
A699	18261	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8+9)+A+B$	$B-A98*-7-(6+5-4321)$
A69A	18262	$-1-2+34*-56*-7-89-A*B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4+3*2+1$
A69B	18263	$-1+2*-345+6+78*(-9-A)*-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4+3^2-1$
A6A0	18264	$1-2*(3-(4^5+6-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6-543*(2+1)$
A6A1	18265	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6-7*-8)+9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6^5+4*3)/(2+1)$
A6A2	18266	$123+4567+8*-9A*-B$	$B+A-9*8*7+6/5^4(4-3^2)-1$
A6A3	18267	$1-2-3+(4-(5*6+7+89A))*-B$	$B+A987-(-6*5-4+321)$
A6A4	18268	$-1+2*(-3+4^5+6/(7-8))*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*54*3*2+1$
A6A5	18269	$-1*2*(3-4^5+6)^4(-7+8)*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+6-54+321)$
A6A6	18270	$-1+2*3456-7*8*-9A+B$	$-B-(-A+9)-(8-7-6-5)*-4*-321$
A6A7	18271	$123-45+678*(9+A)-B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*(6-5-4^3)+2)+1$
A6A8	18272	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^5*6+7*8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*(6-5-4^3)-2^1-1)$
A6A9	18273	$1^2-(-3*(-4^5*-6-7*8)-9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9876-5*-4*-3*-21$
A6AA	18274	$((-1-2)*-3+4^5+6*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A9*-8-7*-6-543*-21$
A6AB	18275	$-1-(-23+456*-7)+89*AB$	$-B+A987+6*-54-3*(2+1)$
A6B0	18276	$-123-4*-567+89AB$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*(6-5/-4^3)-(-2-1))$
A6B1	18277	$1+23+456*7+89*AB$	$-B+A987-(6+54*3*-2)-1$
A6B2	18278	$1*(23-(-4+5))*6-(-78*9+AB)$	$B+A987-(6*54+3+21)$
A6B3	18279	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7*8)-9+A+B$	$-B*-A+9+(-8-7*6^4(5-4+3))*-2^1$
A6B4	18280	$-1-2*(3+(-4*5*-6+7)*-8*9)+A-B$	$-B+A-98+7-6*-5*(432-1)$
A6B5	18281	$-1+((-2+3^4)*-5+6)*(-7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6+54-321$
A6B6	18282	$-1*-2*(34-5-(678-9*A))*-B$	$-B+A987-6-5*(43+21)$
A6B7	18283	$-1+(-2-3*-4^5)*6+(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65*(-4-3+2*1)$
A6B8	18284	$12*(34-56-7-8+9AB)$	$-B+A987+65-4-321$
A6B9	18285	$1+(-2-3*-4^5)*6+(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9*8*7*6+5*4)*3*2^1$
A6BA	18286	$-1*-2*(-3-(-4567-8-9AB))$	$-B+A987-(6*54-3+2)+1$
A6BB	18287	$(1-((2+3)^4+5^6+7))/-8*9+A-B$	$B-A9-8-7-6*5*432*-1$
A700	18288	$1-2^3*(4-5*(6*7+8))*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(6-5-4^3)+2*1$
A701	18289	$-1+2*(345+6)*7+8*9AB$	$-B-A-9/-8*(7+(6+5)^4)*(3^1-2+1)$
A702	18290	$-1+2*(-3+4^5+6/(7-8))*9+A+B$	$-B+A987+6+54*(-3-2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A703	18291	$-1+2-3*(-4^5*6-(-7*8+9))+A-B$	$B+A987-6+54-321$
A704	18292	$-1+23*456-78*-9+AB$	$-B+A987+65-(-4+321)$
A705	18293	$123-45-678*(-9-A)+B$	$BA98-7*-6-543*(2+1)$
A706	18294	$1-23*-456-78*-9+AB$	$-B-A9+8+7+6*5*432-1$
A707	18295	$1-2-(-3*-4^5*6-(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$BA+9-8*7*-6*(5+43+2*-1)$
A708	18296	$(-1-2*(3-4^5)-(-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98+7*-6*(5+4)*-3*-2*1$
A709	18297	$-123*(-4-5-6+7+8*(9-A)-B)$	$B+A-9+(-8-7)*(6-(-5*(4+3))^2/1)$
A70A	18298	$-12*(-34-(-5+6+7+89A-B))$	$-BA-9-8+7+6*5*(432+1)$
A70B	18299	$-1+(-2-3*-4^5)*6-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6+54*-3*2-1$
A710	18300	$1-2*(3-(4^5-6+7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6*-54-3-2-1$
A711	18301	$-1+2-(3+4+5)*(-6-78-9AB)$	$B-(-A987-6)-5*(4-3*-21)$
A712	18302	$(-1+2-3*-4^5)*6+(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6*54-(3+2)+1$
A713	18303	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6)-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6+54-321$
A714	18304	$-1-(-2*(-3-4^5/(6-7)))+8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6*54-(3-2+1)$
A715	18305	$(1+2+3)^4*(5+(-6+7)/(8+9))+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8)*7*(6-5*4^3/2)^4$
A716	18306	$1-(-2*(-3-4^5*(6-7))+8)*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6*54)-(-3+2+1)$
A717	18307	$-1-((-2-3*4^5)*6-(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$BA98+76*5*-4-321$
A718	18308	$1-2+34*(-56*-7+8-9)-AB$	$B+A987+6*-54-(-3+2-1)$
A719	18309	$1-((-2-3*4^5)*6-(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$-BA+9-8-76*5*(-4-(32-1))$
A71A	18310	$-1-(23+5)+67*(89+AB)$	$B+A-9*-8*((-7+6+5)*4^3-2)+1$
A71B	18311	$(-1-2/3+4^5(5+6-7))*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8-7*6)*-5*(4^3-2*1)$
A720	18312	$1-234-5-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987-(-6+54*3*2*1)$
A721	18313	$-1+2-3*-4^5*6*7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-65+4*-3*21$
A722	18314	$1-23+4*(5-(-6-7-8)+9)*AB$	$B+A987+65+4-321$
A723	18315	$-1-23*-456+789-AB$	$-B-A+9876-543*2*1$
A724	18316	$-1*(2-34)*(-567+89A+B)$	$-B-A+9876-(543*-2-1)$
A725	18317	$1-23*-456+789-AB$	$B+A+9*(8+(7*6-(-5+4)*3)^2)-1$
A726	18318	$(-1+2-3*-4^5)*6-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6*(5*4*-3-2*-1)$
A727	18319	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5*6)*(-7+8)*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987-6-(-5-4)*-32-1$
A728	18320	$-1-23+4+5-6*7*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987+6*(-54+3+2+1)$
A729	18321	$-1*(2+3*(-4^5+6)*(7+8-9))+A-B$	$-B-A+9*(876+543+21)$
A72A	18322	$1-2-3*(-4^5+6)*(7+8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6*(54-3)+2*-1$
A72B	18323	$-12-3+4*(-56+78+9)*AB$	$B+A987+6*(-54+3)-2+1$
A730	18324	$1^2-3*(-4^5+6)*(7+8-9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*-7*(6-5*-4^3+2-1)$
A731	18325	$-1-2*-3*-45+67*(89+AB)$	$-B+A+9-87-6*5*432*1$
A732	18326	$12*(34-56-(78-9AB))$	$-B*(-A98-7+65)-(43-21)$
A733	18327	$1-2*(3+45+678)*9-A*-B$	$-B+A987+65+4321$
A734	18328	$123+45*67-89A*-B$	$-B*-A-9+(8+7)^6*5^4-4+3-2+1$
A735	18329	$((1+2)^3+4*5)*-6*(7-8*9)+A-B$	$-BA-9-8*-7*6*(5-(-43+2-1))$
A736	18330	$1+2*(3+(-4^5+6^8(-7+8)))*-9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-87+6*5*-432+1$
A737	18331	$1-((-2-3*4^5)*6-(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-6*5*-4-321$
A738	18332	$-1+23*456+(-78-9)*-A-B$	$-B+A987-65*4-3-21$
A739	18333	$1*-23*(-456+78-(9A+B))$	$BA98-7*-65*-4-3*21$
A73A	18334	$1-23*(-456-(-78+9A)-B)$	$B+A987+6*-54+3+21$
A73B	18335	$-12+34*56*7*(-8+9)-AB$	$-B+A+9876+543*-2*-1$
A740	18336	$-1-23*-456+789A*-B$	$-B-A9-8*-7-6*-5*-432*-1$
A741	18337	$1+2-3*-4^5*6-7*(8+9)+A+B$	$B*(A9-8+765-(-4-321))$
A742	18338	$(-1+2)*-3*(-4^5*6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65*-4+3-21$
A743	18339	$123-4+(-5+6-7-8)*-9A*B$	$-B-A+(-9*8*7+6)*(5+4^3/2-1)$
A744	18340	$12*(3-45+67+89A+B)$	$-B-A+9-8*(7*6+5)^4(4^3-2*1)$
A745	18341	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$BA98+76-543*(2+1)$
A746	18342	$1-2+34*56*7-(-8+9A+B)$	$B+A987+6*(-54-3*2*-1)$
A747	18343	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6)-(-7+8*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6*54)-(-32+1)$
A748	18344	$(-1-2)*((-3-4^5)*6+7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA+9876+54*(-3+21)$
A749	18345	$-12-34*(56-7-8)*-9+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6+(5+4)*(32+1))$
A74A	18346	$-12+3*4*(5-(-6-(78+9AB)))$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7*(-6-5)*(-4-3)*2-1$
A74B	18347	$(-1-2)*(-3-4^5*6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*7*(6-5*4^3/2)^4$
A750	18348	$(-1-2-3*-4^5)*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-87+6*5*432+1$
A751	18349	$-1-2+3*4^5*6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B-A987+(-65-4)*-321$
A752	18350	$1*2+3*4^5*6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6*-5*(4+3^2)-1$
A753	18351	$-1+2-34*56*7-(-8+9A+B)$	$-B+A987-(-65*-4-3*(-2-1))$
A754	18352	$(-1+2)*-3*-4^5*6-(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6*-5*(4+3^2)+1$
A755	18353	$1-23*-4*56+78*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A-(-9*-87-6)-543*-21$
A756	18354	$-1*(23-4)*(-567-8+9)*(-A+B)$	$-B+A987+6-54*(3+2*1)$
A757	18355	$1+2+3*4^5*6-7-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-65*4+3*-2+1$
A758	18356	$-1+23*456+(78-9A)*B$	$B-(-A-9*-8-7)+6*-5*432*-1$
A759	18357	$-1*2-3*(-4^5*6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9876-543*-2*1$
A75A	18358	$1-2-3*(-4^5*6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9*8+(7-6+5*4)^3)*2+1$
A75B	18359	$((1-2)^3+4^5(5+6-7))*8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-8+7^6)*-5*-4^4-3*2^4$
A760	18360	$-1*-23*4*(56+78-(9-A)+B)$	$-B-(-A987+65*4)+3-2-1$
A761	18361	$1*2-3*(-4^5*6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-7-6+54*321$
A762	18362	$1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-98+7-6*5*(-432-1)$
A763	18363	$-1-2+3*4^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-54*(3+2)-1$
A764	18364	$-1*2+3*4^5*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65*-4+3+2-1$
A765	18365	$1-2+3*4^5*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65*-4+3-2*-1$
A766	18366	$(-1+2)*-3*-4^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987+65*-4+3-(-2-1)$
A767	18367	$1^2+3*4^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7*(6-54)*-32*-1$
A768	18368	$1*234*(-56+7-(-8-(9A-B)))$	$-B-A+(-9*(-8*7-6+5)+4)*-3*2-1$
A769	18369	$1+2+3*4^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A-(-9+87-654)*(-3+21)$
A76A	18370	$1-(2+34*56*7)-8+9-A*B$	$B-A-(987-654)*(-32-1)$
A76B	18371	$-1+(-2-3*-4^5)*6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7*65*-4-32+1$
A770	18372	$(-1+2-3*-4^5)*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A9*-8*-7-(-6543+2)*1$
A771	18373	$12-34*56*7-(-8-9A)*-B$	$BA-(9+8*(-76-5))*(-4-(-3-21))$
A772	18374	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5-6^8(7-8))*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9-(8+7)-(-6*5*432+1)$
A773	18375	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6)-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-65*4-(3*2+1)$
A774	18376	$-1-2*(-3-4^5-6*(7-8))*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7-6*5^4)*(-3*2+1)$
A775	18377	$1*2/(3+4^5-6)^8(7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B*-A+9-8*-7*(6-5*-4^3)+2*1$
A776	18378	$-1*(-2-3*4^5)*6-7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7*6)*-5*4*3-(2+1)$
A777	18379	$12-34*56*7-8-9A+B$	$B+A+9*(-8+7*6)*-5*-4*3-2^4$
A778	18380	$-1*-2*(-3+4^5+6^8(7-8))*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+6*(5-43-2)*-1)$
A779	18381	$-1-2+3*4^5*6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B-A*98-765*(4+3-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A77A	18382	$12-3*(-4-56*78)-(-9-AB)$	$-B-A9+87+6*-5*-432-1$
A77B	18383	$1-2+3*4^45*6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-65*4+3+2*-1$
A780	18384	$(-1+2)*-3*-4^45*6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7*6)*-5*4*3+2+1$
A781	18385	$1^2+3*4^45*6-7*8+9+A-B$	$B-A+9-8-(7+6*5*(-432+1))$
A782	18386	$-12+34*(-567+89A-B)$	$B+A987+65*-4-(-3-2)-1$
A783	18387	$1*23*(4-56*-7+89-A*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8*(-7*6+5))*4^3-2*1$
A784	18388	$1*2+3*4^45*6-7*8+9-(A-B)$	$-BA+98-(7-6*-5*-432-1)$
A785	18389	$12+34*5+678*(9+A)+B$	$B+A987-6+5-4*-3*-21$
A786	18390	$1+2*(34+5-678-9)*-A-B$	$B+A987+6*(-5-(-4-3))*-21$
A787	18391	$-1*2-3*(-4^45*6+7)-(-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-(-5+4*3*21)$
A788	18392	$1*(234-5-(-67-89A))*B$	$-B*(-A-9)*(-8-(7-65-(43-21)))$
A789	18393	$-1*(2+(-3/4^4-5+6)*(7+8-9))+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(-8+7-6*5)*(4^3+2)*1$
A78A	18394	$1-2-3*(-4^45*6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-6-5*43)-21$
A78B	18395	$-1+2-(-3-45)*6+7+89A*B$	$B+A+(-9^8-7+6)*(-5*(4+3))^2-1$
A790	18396	$-1*(-2-34)*(5*(-6+78)+9+A-B)$	$-B+A987-(6-5*(-43-2)+1)$
A791	18397	$1-((-2-3*4^45)*6+7*8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6-5*(43+2)*1$
A792	18398	$(-1-2)*(3+4^45*6+7-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7*(6+5*4^3+2)^1$
A793	18399	$-1*2-3*(-4^45*6-7-(8+9))+A-B$	$-B+A987+65*-4+32+1$
A794	18400	$1*-2*-34*(-5-(-6+7)+89+AB)$	$-BA+9*876-5+4321$
A795	18401	$-1+2+34*(-567+89A-B)$	$B+A987+6+5-4*3*21$
A796	18402	$(-1-2)*(3-4^45*6+7)-(-8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6*(-5+43-2*-1)$
A797	18403	$1+2+34*(-567-(-89A+B))$	$-B*(-A98-76-54+32-1)$
A798	18404	$-1-2+3*4^45*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6+5*-43-2-1$
A799	18405	$1*(2-3+4)*5*(-67+8+9A*B)$	$-B+A987-6-(-5*-43+2*1)$
A79A	18406	$1-2+3*4^45*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*8*(7-6-5)^4-3*2+1$
A79B	18407	$-12-34*5*(-6-78)-9*AB$	$-B+A987-6-5*43*(2-1)$
A7A0	18408	$-1*-2*3*(-45-6+7)*(-8*-9-AB)$	$BA98-7*65*4*(-3+2)*-1$
A7A1	18409	$1*2+3*4^45*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA-98-7-6*5*(-432+1)$
A7A2	18410	$12*(-34-(5-67)+89A+B)$	$-BA+9*876-(-5-4321)$
A7A3	18411	$1*2-3*(-4^45*6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$-BA98-7*-65*4*-3*-2-1$
A7A4	18412	$1*-2*(3-(-4-5-(678-9A))*-B))$	$-BA98+7*65*4*(3+2+1)$
A7A5	18413	$12+34*5*(-6-7+89)+A-B$	$-BA98+7*65*4*3+2+1$
A7A6	18414	$-1*(-2+345-67+89A)*-B$	$B*(A98+76-5-4+32-1)$
A7A7	18415	$1*2-3*(-4^45*6+7+8-9)+A-B$	$-B-(A9+8*76)-543*-21$
A7A8	18416	$1+2-3*(-4^45*6+7+8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-5*43-21$
A7A9	18417	$-1+(-2-3*-4^45)*6+(7-8)^9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-6)-(-5*-43-2*-1)$
A7AA	18418	$-1-2+34*5*(-6-78)+9*-AB$	$B+A*9-87-6*-5*432*1$
A7AB	18419	$-1-23-4*-567+89AB$	$-B+A987+6-5*43*(2-1)$
A7B0	18420	$-123-45+67*(89+AB)$	$B+A987+65*-4-32*-1$
A7B1	18421	$1-23-4*-567+89AB$	$-B-A+9+8*(7-6-5)^4*3^2+1$
A7B2	18422	$-1*(2-3)*(45-(-6-78))*(-9+AB)$	$-B+A987-(-6-(-5*43+2))^1$
A7B3	18423	$1*2+3*4^45*6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA-98+7-6*-5*(432-1)$
A7B4	18424	$1-2+3*4^45*6-7-8+9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-6-5*(-43+2-1))$
A7B5	18425	$1*2+3*4^45*6-7+8-9+A-B$	$-B*(-A9-8-765-(-4+321))$
A7B6	18426	$1+2+3*4^45*6-7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+(-6-5)*4*(3+2+1)$
A7B7	18427	$-12+3-4-5+(-6-7)*(8-9AB)$	$B+A*-9*-87+6-5*-4*321$
A7B8	18428	$1+2+3*4^45*6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*(7-(6+5)))^4+3+2+1$
A7B9	18429	$-12-(3-4+5+(-6-7))*(-8+9AB))$	$B-A-(9+8*7*(65-43*-2)*-1)$
A7BA	18430	$-12-3+4*567+89AB$	$BA98-7*65*4-3+21$
A7BB	18431	$-1+23*(4+5)*(67-8)+9*AB$	$-B-A*(9-8-7)*65*4-32*1$
A800	18432	$1+(2-3+4-5+6)^7/8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6-5*43+21$
A801	18433	$1+2+3*4^45*6+(7-8)^9+A-B$	$-B+A+9*8*(-7+6+5)^4+3-2+1$
A802	18434	$-1-2+3*4^45*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-(9+8)*-765-(-4+3*-2)*1$
A803	18435	$-1*2+3*4^45*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987-65+4*(-32-1)$
A804	18436	$-12+3+4*567+89AB$	$BA+9876-5*4*3*21$
A805	18437	$1*2-(3+4)-5-(6+7)*(8-9AB)$	$B-A+9*8*-76+543*21$
A806	18438	$-12*3*(45-67*8+9+AB)$	$-B+A987-65-43*(2+1)$
A807	18439	$1+2+(345-67+89A)*B$	$B-(-A987+6*(-5+43)-21)$
A808	18440	$-12-34*56*-7+89-AB$	$B+A987+6-5*43-(2-1)$
A809	18441	$1*2+3*4^45*6+7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A987+6-5*43*(2-1)$
A80A	18442	$1+2*-3+4*567+89AB$	$B*-A+9*(-8*-7+6+5^4)*3+2+1$
A80B	18443	$1-(2+34*5-67*(89+AB))$	$-B+A987-65+4*(-32+1)$
A810	18444	$12-(-3-4*-5-(6+7)*(-8+9AB))$	$-B+A987+6-5*43+21$
A811	18445	$-1-(-2+3-4*567-89AB)$	$-B+A987+65+4*3*-21$
A812	18446	$1+2-(-3+456)*-7+89A*B$	$-B+A987-6*(5-4)*(32-1)$
A813	18447	$1+23*456+789-(-A+B)$	$-BA9+8*-76*(5+4-32+1)$
A814	18448	$1-23*-456+789*(-A+B)$	$-B-A+98*-7+6-543*-21$
A815	18449	$1+234+5*6*(7*89-AB)$	$-B+A*(-98+76)*(5-43-21)$
A816	18450	$-1*(-23+456)*(78+9-AB)$	$BA9+8765-4*-321$
A817	18451	$-1-2-34*56*-7+89-AB$	$B+A+9*8*(-7+6+5)^4-3+2-1$
A818	18452	$-1-2-34*5-(6+7)*(-8-9AB)$	$-B+A+9+8-7*65*(4-32*1)$
A819	18453	$-123+4*-5+67*(89+AB)$	$BA-98+7+6*5*432*1$
A81A	18454	$1-2+3*4^45*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-5*43+21$
A81B	18455	$1+2-3*(4^45*6+7)/(8-9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6*(5-4+32)+1)$
A820	18456	$1^2+3*4^45*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A9-87-6*-5*432-1$
A821	18457	$1*2+3*4^45*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A987+65*-4-3*-21$
A822	18458	$12-3+4*567+89AB$	$B+A+9*8*(7-6-5)^4+3*2-1$
A823	18459	$1-(2+34*5-67*8-9-(-A-B))$	$B+A987-65*(-4+3-2)*-1$
A824	18460	$-1+2+345-(-6+78)*(9+A)*-B$	$-BA*(-9+8*-7)*((-6+5)*4-3*2*-1)$
A825	18461	$12345+6*7*(-8-9-AB)$	$B-(-A987+65+4*32*1)$
A826	18462	$1^2-3*(-4^45*6+7-(8+9))+A-B$	$B-(-A987+65)-4*32+1$
A827	18463	$1*2-3*(-4^45*6+7-(8+9))+A-B$	$BA+98*(76+54)+321$
A828	18464	$-123-4-5+67*(89+AB)$	$BA98+7*-6*5*(4+3*2*1)$
A829	18465	$-1*2+(-3/-4^4-5+6)*(7+8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*-7*(6+5+(-4*-3)^2)-1$
A82A	18466	$-12*(-345-678-9+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8)*-7*(6+5+(-4*3)^2)^1$
A82B	18467	$-1*(-2-3*4^45)*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA+9-87+6*5*432-1$
A830	18468	$-1*-23*(-4-5)*(6-78-(-9-(-A+B)))$	$-B+A987-6+54*-3+2*-1$
A831	18469	$1-23*-456+789+A+B$	$-B*(-A98+7-(65+43+2))^1$
A832	18470	$(-1/-2-3*-4^45+6)*(7+8-9)+A-B$	$-B-A9*8-7*65*4*-3+21$
A833	18471	$1*2-(-3*(4^45*6+7)-(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A-9*8+(7-6+5*4)^3*2^1$
A834	18472	$-1-23+45+(6+7)*(-8+9AB)$	$-B+A987-6+54*-3+2*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A835	18473	-1+23-4*-567+89AB	-B*-A-9*(-8+7*6)*-5*4*3+2+1
A836	18474	-123-4+5+67*(89+AB)	B+A987+6*(5-4-32+1)
A837	18475	1+23-4*-567+89AB	-BA+9876-5-4*-321
A838	18476	-1*2+3*4^5*6+7*8-9+A-B	B-A*9*8-76-543*-21
A839	18477	1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8-9+A-B	BA+9876+543*2-1
A83A	18478	(-1-2)*(-3-4^5)*6+7/(8-9)+A-B	BA+9876-543*-2*1
A83B	18479	1^2+3*4^5*6+7*8-9+A-B	BA+9876+543*2+1
A840	18480	1*2*3*4*(-56+7+8-9-A)*-B	-B*A*(-98+76+5)*-4*(-3+2-1)
A841	18481	12+3-(-456*7+89A*-B)	-B-A9-(87-6)*54*-3-2-1
A842	18482	-123+4+5+67*(89+AB)	-B+A987-6*(5+43-21)
A843	18483	1^2-3*(-4^5*6+7)+8*9+A-B	BA-98+7-6*5*(-432-1)
A844	18484	1+2-34*-56*7*(-8+9)-(A-B)	BA+9*-87-(6+543*-21)
A845	18485	1+2-3*(-4^5*6+7)+8*9+A-B	B-A+9+8*7+6*5*-432-1
A846	18486	1*(-2-3-4)*(5-6*7*8-9AB)	B+A987+6-5*(4+32)*1
A847	18487	(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6)+7*8+9+A-B	B+A9-87+6*5*(432+1)
A848	18488	(1+2*3+4)*5*6*7*8+9+A-B	-B+A987-65+43*-2-1
A849	18489	-1-234*(-5+6)*-7*8-9+AB	B+A987-6-54*3-2-1
A84A	18490	-1+23-456*-7-89A*-B	B+A987-6+54*-3-2*1
A84B	18491	(-1-2)*(-3-4^5*6+7)+8*9+A-B	B+A987-(6+54*3+2-1)
A850	18492	1+23-456*-7+89A*B	B+A987-6-54*-3*(-2+1)
A851	18493	-123+4*5+67*(89+AB)	B+A987-(6+54*3-2+1)
A852	18494	-1-2-3+45+(6+7)*(-8+9AB)	-B-A+(-9-8*-7-6*5^4)*(-3*2+1)
A853	18495	1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8+9+A-B	-B+A987-6+54*3+21
A854	18496	12+34*56*7-(8-9-(A+B))	BA-9+8*-7+6*5*-432-1
A855	18497	1^2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	-B+A987-6+5*4-32+1
A856	18498	1*234-5+678*(9+A)+B	BA+9-87+6*-5*(-432-1)
A857	18499	-1+2-34*-56*7+8-(-9+A)+B	-B-A-9+8+(7-6+5*4)^3*2-1
A858	18500	1*2*(-3+45)*(67-(-89+A-B))	B-A*-9*(-87+65*4)-(-32-1)
A859	18501	1*(23-(4+567+89))*(-A-B)	-B+A-(-9-87)+6*5*(432-1)
A85A	18502	1-2-3*(-4^5*6-(7+8+9))+A-B	-B+A987-6-5*(4+3+21)
A85B	18503	-1-2-34*-56*7-89+AB	-B-A+9-8+(7-6+5*4)^3*2+1
A860	18504	1234*(5-6)*(7-8-9-A+B)	-B+A987-6-5+4*32-1
A861	18505	1-2-34*-56*7-89+AB	B+A987+(-6-(-5+4))*3(32-1)
A862	18506	1+2-(-3-45)-(6+7)*(8-9AB)	-B+A*-9*-87-6+5432-1
A863	18507	-1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8+9+A-B	-B+A987+6-54*3+21
A864	18508	12*(345+678-(9-A*-B))	-BA98+7654*-3*(-2+1)
A865	18509	1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	-BA98-7654*-3+2-1
A866	18510	(-1+2)*-3*-4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	B+A+9+8*7*6*5*(4+3*2+1)
A867	18511	1^2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	B+A987-65-43*2*1
A868	18512	1*2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	-B+A987-(65+4)*3*-21
A869	18513	1+2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A-B	-B*(-A9+87+65)*(4-32+1)
A86A	18514	-1-2*(3-(4^5+6+7-8)*9)+A-B	-B-(-A987-(6+5+43*(-2-1)))
A86B	18515	(-1-2)*((-3-4^5)*6+7-(8+9))+A-B	-B+A987-(65+43+21)
A870	18516	(-1+2-3*-4^5)*6+7*8*9+A-B	-B+A987-(6-5+4*32-1)
A871	18517	1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A+B	-B-A9+87*-6-543*-21
A872	18518	(-1+2)*-3*-4^5*6+7*8*9+A+B	B+A(9+8-7*(6-5*4-3))^2+1
A873	18519	-1+2+34*56*7+8+9+A+B	-B+A987+65*4-321
A874	18520	-1*(-2-3)*(-4*(-5-678)-9-AB)	-B-(-A987+65)-(-4+3*21)
A875	18521	((-1-2)*(-3-4^5)+6)*(7+8-9)+A-B	-B-A+9*876-5+4321
A876	18522	-1*(2+34)*(5+67-89)*(A+B)	-B+A+9-8+(7-6+5*4)^3*2*1
A877	18523	1-(2-3*(4^5*6+7)-8*9)+A-B	-B+A987-(6+54+3*21)
A878	18524	12+34*5*(6-7+89)+A*B	B-(-A987+6)-5*(4+3+21)
A879	18525	1^2-(-3*(4^5*6+7)-8*9)+A-B	B-(-A987-(65-4*(-3+21)))
A87A	18526	-123+45-67*(-89-AB)	BA98-7*-6*-5-4*321
A87B	18527	-1*-2*(3+(4^5+6+7-8)*9)+A-B	B+A987-6-(5-4*32*-1)
A880	18528	1*2-(-3*(4^5*6+7)-8*9)-(A-B)	-B+A-(-98+76*5*-432*-1)
A881	18529	(1+2*3)^4+5^6+7*8*9+A-B	B-A*-9*87+(6-5432)*-1
A882	18530	((1^2+3)^4+5)*(6+7*8+9)+A-B	-B-A-9*(-8*-7+6+5^4)*-3+2*1
A883	18531	1-2+3*4^5*6+7*8*9+A+B	-B-A+9*876-(-5-4321)
A884	18532	(-1-2)*(-3-4^5)*6+7*8-9+A-B	-B+A987-(6+5*(43-21))
A885	18533	(-1-2)*(-3-(4^5*6+7))+8*9+A-B	-BA98-7654*-3+21
A886	18534	-1+23*456-7*(-8-9)*A+B	B+A987-65+4*3*21
A887	18535	1*(-23-4+56*(-78+9A))*B	-B+A987+6-54-3*21
A888	18536	-12*(34+5-67+8+9A*-B)	B+A+(-9-8*-7-6*5^4)*(-3*2+1)
A889	18537	(-1-2)*((-3-4^5)*6+7-(8+9))+A+B	B-(-A987-(65-(43+21)))
A88A	18538	-1-(-2+(3+4)^-5*-6*7^8)*9+A-B	-B+A987-(65+43*2*1)
A88B	18539	-1+2*(34+5)*(67+8+9-A*-B)	B-A*9*87-6*(-543*2-1)
A890	18540	1-(-2+(3+4)^-5*-6*7^8)*9+A-B	B+A*-9*-87-(6-5432+1)
A891	18541	(-1+2*(3+4))*5+6-(7-8)*9+A-B	B+A987-65*-4-321
A892	18542	-1+2*(-3+4^5+(-6+7)*8)*9+A+B	-B+A987+6*(5-(4-3)-21)
A893	18543	((-1-2)*(-3-4^5)+6)*(7+8-9)+A+B	B-A+9*876-5+4321
A894	18544	-1+2*(3-(4^5+6/(7-8))*9)+A-B	B+A+9-8+(7-6+5*4)^3*2*1
A895	18545	12+34*-5*(6+7-89)+AB	-B+A-9+8*-76-543*-21
A896	18546	1+2*(3-(-4^5+6/(7-8))*9)+A-B	-B-(-A9+8+7)-6*5*-432+1
A897	18547	-1-(2-3*4^5*6-7*(8+9))+A-B	B-A-9+8*-76-543*-21
A898	18548	(-1-2-3*-4^5)*6-(-7-8)*9+A-B	-B-(-A987+65)-(-4+32+1)
A899	18549	-1*-23*(456+7-(-8-9-A)+B)	-B+A987-(65+4+32*1)
A89A	18550	-12*(34-56+7-8-9A*B)	-B+A987-(65-(-4-32))+1
A89B	18551	-1*(2-(-34-5)+6*-7+8)*-9AB	B-A*-9*87*(6-5)*(-4-(-3-2)+1)
A8A0	18552	1*2*3*-4*(-567-(89-AB))	-B+A9-(-8-7-(-6*5*-432-1))
A8A1	18553	1+2*3*-4*(-567-89+AB)	B+A-(-9-87-6*5*-432*-1)
A8A2	18554	1-2*(3+(-4^5-6+7-8)*9)-(A-B)	-B+A987-6-5-43*2-1
A8A3	18555	1+(-2-3*-4^5)*6-(-7-8)*9+A-B	BA98-7-65*(4-3+21)
A8A4	18556	-1-23*-456+789-A*-B	-B+A987-65+4-(32+1)
A8A5	18557	(-1-2*(3-4^5)+6+7*8)*9+A-B	-B+A987-(-6+5)+4*(-3-21)
A8A6	18558	1+(-2*(3+4^5/(6-7))+8)*9+A-B	-B+A987-65+4-32+1
A8A7	18559	1-((-2-3*4^5)*6+(-7-8)*9)-(A+B)	-B+A987-65-4-3-21
A8A8	18560	1*-2*34*(5-(-6+7)-89-AB)	B-(-A987+65)-(-43+2*1)
A8A9	18561	-1-((-2-3*4^5)*6-7*(8+9))+A-B	-B-(-A987+6)-(-54+32-1)
A8AA	18562	-1*((-2-3*4^5)*6-7*(8+9))+A-B	BA98-7*(-6-5)*(-43+21)
A8AB	18563	(-1-2)*(3-4^5*6-7*8+9)+A-B	B+A987-65-(43-2+1)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A8B0	18564	$-12^*(3-(45-(6-7)))*(-89+AB)$	$-B+A987-6+5+43^*-2-1$
A8B1	18565	$1-(23+45)-67^*(-89-AB)$	$B-(-A987-(65-43))-(2-1)$
A8B2	18566	$((1^2-3+4)^A(5+6)+7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6+5^*(-43+21)$
A8B3	18567	$1^2-3^*-4^A5^*6-(7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6^*5)-(4^*32+1)$
A8B4	18568	$-1-23^*-456+7^*8-9^*-AB$	$-B+A987-65+4^*3^*-2+1$
A8B5	18569	$1-2^*(-3+4+5+678-9A)^*-B$	$BA98+7+65^*(-43+21)$
A8B6	18570	$-1-2+34^*-56^*-7-(8+9)-A^*-B$	$-B+A987-(6+5+43)-21$
A8B7	18571	$(-1/-2-3^*-4^A5)^*6-(7-8)^*9-(A-B)$	$-B-(-A987-6-(54-32)+1)$
A8B8	18572	$(-1+2-3^*-4^A5)^*6-(7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+65+4-(32+1))$
A8B9	18573	$-1+2^*(-34+5)+67^*(89+AB)$	$-B-(-A987-6-(54-32+1))$
A8BA	18574	$-12-(3+45-67^*(89+AB))$	$-B-A+9^*8+(7-6+5^*4)^3*2+1$
A8BB	18575	$-12+3-(456+78^*(9+A))^*-B$	$B+A-9-((-8-7)^*(-6+5^A4)+3)^*2-1$
A900	18576	$1^*-23^*(-4-567+8-(9A+B))$	$B-(-A987+65)-(-4^*3+21)$
A901	18577	$-1-23^*-456+789+AB$	$-B+A987+6+5+43^*2^*-1$
A902	18578	$-12^*(3-(4+5)+6-(78+9AB))$	$-B+A987-65+4^*3-21$
A903	18579	$1-((-2-3^*4^A5)^*6+(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$B+A987-65+4-32^*1$
A904	18580	$((1+2)^A3+4^A5+6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+65-4)-(32-1)$
A905	18581	$(-1-2)^*(3+4^A5^*6-7^*8)-9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(6+5)-(43+21)$
A906	18582	$1^2*4^*(-3-45+6-7)^*(8^*(9A)-B)$	$B+A987-(-6-54-32)^*-1$
A907	18583	$-1-((-2-3^*4^A5)^*6-7^*(8+9))+A+B$	$B+A987-6-54-(32-1)$
A908	18584	$(-1-2^A(3+4))^*(-5-6-7)^*8+9+A-B$	$BA+98+7^*65^*(-4+32)^*1$
A909	18585	$-12-34-5-67^*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987-(-6^*-5+43+2^*1)$
A90A	18586	$-1+2-34^*56^*-7-89^*(A-B)$	$-B+A987-(-6^*-5+43+2-1)$
A90B	18587	$1-2-(-3^*-4^A5^*6+(-7-8)^*9)+A+B$	$B+A987-(65+43-21)$
A910	18588	$-1^*2-3^*(-4^A5^*6-7^*8)-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-6+54)+3-21$
A911	18589	$1+2-34^*-56^*7+89-(A-B)$	$-B-(-A987+65+4-3+2-1)$
A912	18590	$(-1+2)^*-3^*(-4^A5^*6-7^*8)-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+65)-(-4+3^*2)+1$
A913	18591	$-12+3-45-(-6-7)^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A987-6+5-43-21$
A914	18592	$-12^*(3+45+6-78-9A^*B)$	$-B+A987+65-(-4^*-32+1)$
A915	18593	$1-(2+34^*56^*-7+8)-(9-AB)$	$-B+A987-(-6+5+43+21)$
A916	18594	$1+2/(3+4^A5+6)^A(7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6-54+32^*-1$
A917	18595	$1+2-3^*(-4^A5^*6-7^*8)-9-(A-B)$	$B+A987+6-54-32+1$
A918	18596	$-12+34^*-56^*-7+8-9+AB$	$-B-A+9876-5+4^*321$
A919	18597	$1+2+3-45+67^*(89+AB)$	$-B-(-A987+6+54-(-3+2^*1))$
A91A	18598	$123+4^*-5-(-6-7)^*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A987-6-54-3+2+1$
A91B	18599	$-1+234^*-5+(-67-89)^*-A^*B$	$-B+A^*(9-(-876-(-5+432)))+1$
A920	18600	$((1-2^A3)^A4+(-5-6)^*7)^*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6-54+3-2+1$
A921	18601	$1-234^*5-(67+89)^*A^*-B$	$-B+A987-65-4^*-3-2^*1$
A922	18602	$1^*-2^*(34-(-5+67-89))^*-AB$	$-B+A987-(-6+54-3-(2-1))$
A923	18603	$-1^*-23^*(-4+567-89-(A-B)))$	$B+A987-6-5-(43+21)$
A924	18604	$-1+23^*456+78-9^*-AB$	$-B+A987-6-5-43+2^*-1$
A925	18605	$-1-23^*-456+7+(-89-A)^*-B$	$-B-(-A987-6)-(-54+3-2^*-1)$
A926	18606	$-1+23-4^*(56^*-78+9AB)$	$-B+A987+6-54-3-2+1$
A927	18607	$-1-23^*-456-(7-89A-B)$	$-B+A987-65+4^*(3-(-2+1))$
A928	18608	$1-(-2345+6)-(7+89)^*-AB$	$-B+A987+6-54-3+2-1$
A929	18609	$1-23-4-5-67^*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987-65-4+3-2-1$
A92A	18610	$-1+(-2+(-3-4^*5)^*6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6^*5+4^*(3-21)$
A92B	18611	$1+2-3^*(-4^A5^*6-7^*8)+9+A-B$	$B+A987-65-(-4+3)-(2+1)$
A930	18612	$1+2-34+5+67^*(89+AB)$	$B+A987-(65-43)^*(2+1)$
A931	18613	$-1+(-2+3+4)^A5^*6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(6-5)-43-(2+1)$
A932	18614	$1-(-2-34^*(5+67)-89AB)$	$B+A987-6-54-3^*2^*1$
A933	18615	$1-((2+3)^A4^*-5^*6-(-7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-(6+5)-(-4-32^*-1)$
A934	18616	$(1+2^A3-4)^A5^*6+(-7-8)^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A9-8^*-7+6^*5^*-432^*-1$
A935	18617	$12+3^*45^*(67+8-(-9-A-B))$	$-B+A987-65-(-43+21)$
A936	18618	$123+4^*567+89AB$	$-B+A987-6+5-(43-2^*1)$
A937	18619	$1+23-45-67^*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987+6^*(-5-(-4+3))-(-2+1)$
A938	18620	$1+2345+6-(-7-89)^*AB$	$-B+A987-6-54-3+21$
A939	18621	$-1+23^*456+7-(-89A-B)$	$-B+A987+6-5-(43-2)+1$
A93A	18622	$1-23^*-456-(-7+8-9A)^*B$	$-B+A987-(6+5-4+32+1)$
A93B	18623	$12-34+5-67^*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987-6-5+4+32^*-1$
A940	18624	$-1^*2-3^*(-4^A5^*6+7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-6+5-4-32-1$
A941	18625	$12+34^*(5+67)+89AB$	$B+A987-(-6-5+43+21)$
A942	18626	$1-2-34^*5^*(6-78)+9AB$	$-B+A987+6-5-4-32-1$
A943	18627	$1^2-3^*(-4^A5^*6+7-8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-6-5+43+2)+1$
A944	18628	$1^2-3^*(-4^A5^*6+7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-(54+3-(-2+1))$
A945	18629	$((1+2^*3)^A4+5-6^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-5-43+2-1$
A946	18630	$1^*23^*(456-78-(-9-AB))$	$-B+A987+6-(-5+(-43+2))^*-1$
A947	18631	$-1-2-(3-4-(56+78)^*9A)-B$	$B+A987-(6+5)-43+2+1$
A948	18632	$-12+3+4-5-67^*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987+6-(-5-4-3+21)$
A949	18633	$-1^*(-2+(-3-4^*5)^*6^*(-7-8)^*9)-(A-B)$	$-B+A987-6-5+4^*3^*-2^*1$
A94A	18634	$-1+2^*34^*56-(-789A+B)$	$-B+A987-(65-4)-(-32-1)$
A94B	18635	$123-456^*-7-89A^*-B$	$-B+A987-(6-(-54+32)+1)$
A950	18636	$-12-3+4+5+67^*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987-6-54+32^*1$
A951	18637	$1-((2+3)^A4^*-5^*6-(-7-8)^*9)+A+B$	$B+A987-6-(-5+43+2-1)$
A952	18638	$(-1+2+(-3-4^*5)^*6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-6+54-3-21)$
A953	18639	$123^*(45-6-(-78+9A+B))$	$B+A987-65-(-4+3)+21$
A954	18640	$-1^*2^*34^*(-5-6-7-89+A^*-B)$	$-B+A987-65-(-43+2^*1)$
A955	18641	$-1+2+34^*(-5-678+9AB)$	$BA98-76-5+4^*-321$
A956	18642	$-1+2-3-(4-5)^*67^*(89+AB)$	$B+A987+6^*5-(-4-3)-21$
A957	18643	$1-(-2^*(3+4^A5+6)-(7+8))^*9+A+B$	$-B+A987-(6+5)-(-4^*-3+2^*1)$
A958	18644	$1^*(-23-(45+6-7))^*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987-(-6-5)+4-32-1$
A959	18645	$-1^*2+(-3-(4+5^*6))^*-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(65-43-2-1)$
A95A	18646	$1+2-3^*4-(56+78)^*-9A+B$	$B+A987-65-4+32-1$
A95B	18647	$-1-2-3-(-4-5)+67^*(89+AB)$	$B+A987-6-(5+4)-(-3+21)$
A960	18648	$1^*-2^*3^*-4^*(5^*-6+78^*9-A-B)$	$B+A9876+5-4^*-321$
A961	18649	$1^*2+(-3-(4+5^*6))^*-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-6+54-32-1)$
A962	18650	$1+2+3^*(-4+5)+67^*(89+AB)$	$B-(-A987-6-(-5-4)-(-32+1))$
A963	18651	$((1+2^*3)^A4+5-6^*7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$BA98-76-(-5+4^*321)$
A964	18652	$12+3-4-5+67^*(89+AB)$	$BA98-7-65-4^*321$
A965	18653	$-12+3-4^*-5+67^*(89+AB)$	$B+A987-6-(5+43)+21$
A966	18654	$12+34^*(-5-678+9AB)$	$B+A987-6+5+4-32-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
A967	18655	$-1*(23-45-(-6-7))*(8+9AB)$	$B+A987-65+4+32*1$
A968	18656	$-1+2+(3-4)^2*(-56-78)*9A+B$	$-B+A987-6-(5-(4-3))+2*-1$
A969	18657	$1*23*(-4+567-89-A+B)$	$-BA-9-8+7*6*(-5-(4-321))$
A96A	18658	$-1-23*(-456+7-8)+9A*B$	$-B+A987-6-5-4+3-2*-1$
A96B	18659	$12345-6*(789-A*B)$	$-B-(-A987+6)-(5-4+3)+2-1$
A970	18660	$1*(-2+3+5-6-7)*8*(9A-B)$	$B+A987+6+5-4-32+1$
A971	18661	$-1-(-23+4+5)-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987-6-5+4-(-3+21)$
A972	18662	$12*(3-4)*(5-67-(89A-B))$	$-B-(-A987+6+5-4-3+2*1)$
A973	18663	$1+23-(-4+5+67*(-89-AB))$	$B+A987-6-(-5+43-21)$
A974	18664	$-1-(-2+(-3-4-5*6)*7*8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5-(-4+3-2*1)$
A975	18665	$-1-2*(3-456)-78*9*(-A-B)$	$B+A987+6-5-43+21$
A976	18666	$-1*2-3*(-4^5*6-(7+8*9))+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+65)-4*321$
A977	18667	$-12345-6*7*8*(-9A-B)$	$-B+A987-(6-5)+4-3-2+1$
A978	18668	$-1-23*-456-78+9AB$	$-B+A987*(65-43-21)$
A979	18669	$-1-23+45+67*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987+65-43-21$
A97A	18670	$-1+23+(4-5)*-67*(89+AB)$	$-B-(-A987+65-4-3*2*1)$
A97B	18671	$1-(2-3-4)^5*6-7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-(-5-4-3)-21$
A980	18672	$(1-(2+3)^4)*-5*6-7*8+9A-B$	$B+A987-6*5-43-(-2-1)$
A981	18673	$-1+(-2*(-3-4^5)+6+7+8)*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6*5-4*3-2+1)$
A982	18674	$(-1-2*(3-(4^5+6+7))+8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9+87-6*-5*432*1$
A983	18675	$-1-2+3+4*5+(-6-7)*(-8-9AB)$	$B+A987+6+5-43+21$
A984	18676	$1*(-2-3*45)*6(7-8-(9-(-A-B)))$	$-B+A987+6-5*4-3+21$
A985	18677	$-1+2-3*(-4+56)*(-78-9)+A*-B$	$B-A-98*(-76-(-5+43)-21)$
A986	18678	$12+3456+(7-89)*-AB$	$-B+A987+6+5+4-3+2*-1$
A987	18679	$(1+(2+3)^4)*-5*6/(7-8)+9-A*B$	$B-(-A987+6+5-4*(-3+2+1))$
A988	18680	$(-1-2)*((-3-4^5)*6-7*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6-(-5-4+3*-2))$
A989	18681	$1+23-(-4-5)-67*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987-6-(5+4)-(-3-21)$
A98A	18682	$-1+23+45*(-6+78-9A)*-B$	$B+A987+6+5*4+3+2+1$
A98B	18683	$-1-(2-3-4)^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6-5+43-21$
A990	18684	$-1*23*-4*(-5+67-8+9A-B)$	$B-(-A987+6)-5-(-4-3)+2*-1$
A991	18685	$1-(2-3-4)^5*6+7-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-5+4+3-2+1$
A992	18686	$-12+3+45-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987-(6-5)*(4-3)-(-2+1)$
A993	18687	$(1^2+3)^4*((-5+6+7)*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-6+5+4-32-1$
A994	18688	$1-2+3+4+5-67*(-89-AB)$	$B+A987+65-4+3*-21$
A995	18689	$1-2-3*(-4^5*6-(7+8*9))+A+B$	$B-(-A987+65-43)+21$
A996	18690	$-1+2*-3+45+67*(89+AB)$	$B+A987+(65-4)*(3-2-1)$
A997	18691	$12345-(-6-7*8*(-9A+B))$	$B+A987+6-5-4+3+2-1$
A998	18692	$1-(-23-4^5)+67*(89+AB)$	$B+A987-65+4-3*-21$
A999	18693	$12-(-34+5)+67*(89+AB)$	$B+A987+6-(5-4+3-2+1)$
A99A	18694	$1-2-(34*56*-7-89)-A*-B$	$B+A987+6-5+4-3+2*1$
A99B	18695	$(-1+2/3-4*-5*(6+7))*8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-65+43-2+1)$
A9A0	18696	$-12+3*-4*-5*6+7+89A*B$	$B-(-A987+6*5-5-(4-3)+21)$
A9A1	18697	$-1-2+3+4+5+(6+7)*(8+9AB)$	$-B+A987-(-65+43-2-1)$
A9A2	18698	$(-1+(2+3)^4*5)*6-7*8+9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987-6+5+4-3-21$
A9A3	18699	$((1^2+3)^4+5+6-7)*8*9-(A+B)$	$B-(-A987-6+5-4-3-2+1)$
A9A4	18700	$-1*2*(-3+45)*6(7-8+9-A*B)$	$-B+A987+6-(-54+32*1)$
A9A5	18701	$-1+2+3+45-67*(-89-AB)$	$-B+A987+6+5+4-32+1$
A9A6	18702	$-1-(2+3)+45-(6+7)*(-8-9AB)$	$-B+A987-6+5-4+32+1$
A9A7	18703	$12-(-34-5)+67*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987+6-(-5+4-3-21)$
A9A8	18704	$12*(3+4+5+6-7-(-89A-B))$	$B+A987+6+5+4-(3+2*-1)$
A9A9	18705	$1-2+3+4+5+6+7*(8+9AB)$	$B+A987-(6+5-(-43-21))$
A9AA	18706	$(1^2+3+4)^5*6-7*8-9A+B$	$-B+A987+6-5+4*3+21$
A9AB	18707	$(-1+(2+3)^4*5-6)*(7+8-9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+6-5)-(-4+3-21)$
A9B0	18708	$12-3+4+5+67*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987-6+5+4+32-1$
A9B1	18709	$12-34*-56*7+89-A*-B$	$BA98-7+65*4*3*-2*-1$
A9B2	18710	$-1-23*(456+78-9AB)$	$-B+A987-(-65-4+32)-1$
A9B3	18711	$-1*23*(456+78-9AB)$	$-B*(-A-(-9+8-76))*(5-43+21)$
A9B4	18712	$1-(2^3-4*-5*(-6-7)*8*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5+4+32+1$
A9B5	18713	$1*-2^3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987+65-43-2-1$
A9B6	18714	$-1-23*(-4-(567-89))-AB$	$B-(-A987-6)-(-5+4*-3-2+1)$
A9B7	18715	$1-2-3+4*5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(6-5-43+21)$
A9B8	18716	$1+23+4*(56+7)*8*(9A-B)$	$-B-(-A987-6)-(-54-3)-21$
A9B9	18717	$-1+2-3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5+43-2-1$
A9BA	18718	$-1234-567*(89-AB)$	$-B+A987*(6-5)+43-2+1$
A9BB	18719	$1-(-2+34*56*-7-89-AB)$	$B+A987+65-43+2+1$
AA00	18720	$1*(-2-3)*4*(-567-8-9A-B)$	$-B+A987+65+4*3*-2-1$
AA01	18721	$((1^2+3)^4+5+6-7)*8*9-(A-B)$	$B-(-A987-6)-(-5-4-32*1)$
AA02	18722	$(-1+2)*3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-6+5-4+32-1$
AA03	18723	$-12-(345+6+78*(-9A)*B)$	$B+A987-6+5+(4-32)*-1$
AA04	18724	$-1+(2+3)^4*5*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+6-54+3-2+1)$
AA05	18725	$(1-2*3)^4*5*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B-(-A987+65-4*(3+21))$
AA06	18726	$1+(2+3)^4*5*6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76*-5*-4+32*-1$
AA07	18727	$1-23456-7*-8*-9*-AB$	$B+A987+6-(-5-4)-3+21$
AA08	18728	$1+2^3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(6-54-3+2-1)$
AA09	18729	$-1*-2^3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A987-(6+5-43+2-1)$
AA0A	18730	$-1*-2*(-345+6+78*(9A-B))$	$-B-(-A987+6)-(-54-3-2+1)$
AA0B	18731	$(1-(2-3-4)^5)*6-(7+8)-9A-B$	$-B+A987-(-6-5)-(-43-2+1)$
AA10	18732	$1*(23+456)*7*(-8-9-(-A-B))$	$B+A987+6+5+4-(3+21)$
AA11	18733	$-1*2^3-4*-5*(-6-7)*-8*9+A+B$	$B+A987+6+5-(-4-3-21)$
AA12	18734	$1*2*(-34+567+89*(-A-B))$	$B+A987+65+4-32+1$
AA13	18735	$(-1+2+3)*(4+5*(-6-7)*-8*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-65+4)-(-3+21)$
AA14	18736	$1-2*(3+4+5^6/((-7-8)/9))+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6-5+4-32-1)$
AA15	18737	$(1+2)^3*(4*5*6*7*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A987-(6-5)-(-43+2+1)$
AA16	18738	$-1+(2+3)^4*5*6+7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-6-54)+3-2-1$
AA17	18739	$(1-2*3)^4*5*6+7-8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65-(4+3-2+1)$
AA18	18740	$-1+234*5*6+7*89A+B$	$BA98-7+6+5+4*-321$
AA19	18741	$1+2*3*(-4+567)+89A*B$	$B+A987-6+5+43+2-1$
AA1A	18742	$1+(2+3)^4*5*6+7+8-9A-B$	$-B+A987+65-(4-3)+2*-1$
AA1B	18743	$12345-6*(7-8-9*-A*B)$	$B+A987-6+5+43-(-2-1)$
AA20	18744	$-1*-2*-3*-4*(567-8-(9-(-A-B)))$	$B+A987-(6-54+3-(-2+1))$
AA21	18745	$1-2-(-3-4*-5*(-6-7)*8)*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-65)-(-4+3+2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
AA22	18746	$12^* (-3-4-56-(7+8-9AB))$	$B+A987-6-5^*4^*-3+2^*1$
AA23	18747	$1-23^*-456-7-8+9AB$	$-B+A987+65+4-3-(-2+1)$
AA24	18748	$1-2+3^*4^*5^*6/(-7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6+5+4-3+2+1$
AA25	18749	$1-(2-3-4)^*5^*6+(7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6-5-4+3+2+1)$
AA26	18750	$1^*2+3^*4^*5^*6/(-7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6+5-4-3^*-21$
AA27	18751	$1^*2+3^*4^*5^*6/(-7+8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A9^*-87-(65-4)^*-3^*21$
AA28	18752	$1+2+3^*4^*5^*6/(-7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987-(6-(5+3))-(-2+1)$
AA29	18753	$1+(2^*(3+4)+5)^*(6-(7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6^*5-(4-32)^*-1$
AA2A	18754	$-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6+5+4^*-321$
AA2B	18755	$(1^*2^*3+4)^*5^*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A987-6-(5-43)+21$
AA30	18756	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^*6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65+4^*3-2+1$
AA31	18757	$123-(456+78^*(9+A))^*-B$	$B+A987-(-65+4)-(3+2)^*-1$
AA32	18758	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^*6+7-8+9+A-B$	$BA^*9-87^*6-543^*-21$
AA33	18759	$(1-2^*3)^*4^*5^*6-7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A9876-5+4^*321$
AA34	18760	$1^*-2^*(-3-4)^*(56-7+89+A+B)$	$-B-(-A987-6-5+4+3)+21$
AA35	18761	$-1+23^*456-7+8+9AB$	$B+A987+65-4-3+2-1$
AA36	18762	$1^*-2^*3^*45^*(-6-7^*-8+9)^*(A-B)$	$B+A987+65-(4-(-3+2))^*1$
AA37	18763	$1-23^*-456-7+8+9AB$	$BA98+76^*-5^*4-(3-2)^*1$
AA38	18764	$(-1-2^*(3-4^*5+6)+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6+5+4-32^*-1$
AA39	18765	$(1-(2-3-4)^*5)^*6-7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-6+5+4+3+21$
AA3A	18766	$(1-(2+3)^*4)^*-5^*6+7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+65-4+3^*(2-1)$
AA3B	18767	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4+5^*6/(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6-(-5-4-3^*2)+1$
AA40	18768	$-1^*(23-4)^*(567+8+9)^*(A-B)$	$B+A987+6^*(-5-(4+3-21))$
AA41	18769	$1+2^*-3^*-4^*-5^*(567-8-9)^*(-A+B)$	$-B+A987-6+5+4+3^*-2^*-1$
AA42	18770	$-12-34^*5^*6^*7-8+9^*AB$	$B+A987-(-65-4)-(3-2^*1)$
AA43	18771	$1-(2-3-4)^*5^*6+(7-8)^*9+A+B$	$-B+A987+65+4+3-21$
AA44	18772	$1-23-45^*-6^*-7^*-8+9^*-A^*-B$	$B+A987+65+4+(-3+2)^*-1$
AA45	18773	$(1^*2^*3+4)^*5^*6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6^*5-4^*321$
AA46	18774	$-1^*2^*(-3^*-4-5)^*(-6+78-9AB)$	$B+A987-6-5^*(4+3-21)$
AA47	18775	$1+(2^*(3+4)+5)^*(6-(7-8)^*9)+A+B$	$-B+A987+6+5+4+32-1$
AA48	18776	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^*6+7+8+9-(A-B)$	$B+A987-(6-5+4)+3+21$
AA49	18777	$1+2^*(-3+4)-(-56+78^*9)^*(A+B)$	$-B+A987+6+5+4+32+1$
AA4A	18778	$-1+2-3^*(4567+89A^*-B)$	$-B+A987+65-(4-32+1)$
AA4B	18779	$12-34^*56+(7+8)^*9AB$	$-B-(-A987-65+4+32^*-1)$
AA50	18780	$1+2+3^*(-4567-89A^*-B)$	$-B+A987+65-4-(-32-1)$
AA51	18781	$(1+(2+3)^*4)^*-5^*6^*(7-8)^*9-(A-B)$	$B-(-A987-65)-(-4^*3+2^*-1)$
AA52	18782	$(-1+2^*3+4^*5^*6-(6-7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-65-4^*3)+21$
AA53	18783	$-1^*(2-3+4)^*(-56+78+9^*(-A-B))$	$BA98+7^*6+5-4^*321$
AA54	18784	$-12-3^*4-(-5-(6+7))^*(-89+A)^*-B$	$B+A+(-9-8-7^*6)^*(-5/4^*-3+2)+1$
AA55	18785	$12345-6^*(789-AB)$	$B+A987+65-(4+3)+21$
AA56	18786	$-1^*2-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-65-4-32)^*-1$
AA57	18787	$1+2-(-34^*5^*6^*7-8^*9^*AB)$	$B+A987+65+4^*(3-2^*-1)$
AA58	18788	$-12^*(-3+4-5-67-89A+B)$	$B+A987-6^*5^*-4+3-21$
AA59	18789	$1+2^*-3^*(-4-567)-89A^*-B$	$B+A987+6+5+4^*(-3+21)$
AA5A	18790	$1-2+3+(-4+56+78)^*(-9+AB)$	$B+A987+65+4^*-3^*-2-1$
AA5B	18791	$1+2-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*(8+9))+A-B$	$B+A987+6+5^*4+3^*21$
AA60	18792	$1^*23^*(-4+567+8-9A-B)$	$B+A987+65-4^*-3^*2+1$
AA61	18793	$-1-(2-3-4)^*5^*6-7+8^*9-(A+B)$	$B+A987+65+4-3+21$
AA62	18794	$1+(-2+(-3-4-5^*6)^*7)^*-8^*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987+65+4+3+2^*-1$
AA63	18795	$123+4^*-5+67^*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987+65+4+3-(2-1)$
AA64	18796	$1-2^*-3^*4^*-5^*-6^*7+89^*AB$	$-B+A987+65-43^*(-2+1)$
AA65	18797	$1-(2-3-4)^*5^*6+7^*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+65-(-43-2+1)$
AA66	18798	$(1-(2+3)^*4)^*-5^*6+7+8^*9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-65-43)^*-2^*-1$
AA67	18799	$-1^*(2+(3+4)^*5+6-7)/-8^*9^*A^*B$	$-B+A987+65+4+3+2+1$
AA68	18800	$1^*-2^*(3+4+56-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B-(-A987-65+4)-(-32+1)$
AA69	18801	$(-1-2^*3)^*(4-5^*6)^*(7+8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987-(6-5+4+3^*-21)$
AA6A	18802	$12^*(-3-4^*-5)^*6+7+8-9+A+B$	$B+A987+65-4-(-32-1)$
AA6B	18803	$-1-23^*(-456-7)+89A+B$	$B+A987+65+4^*3^*(-2-1)$
AA70	18804	$1-2^*(3-4^*5+6-(-7-8))^*9+A-B$	$-BA9+876+543^*21$
AA71	18805	$-1^*(-2+3^*-45-67^*(89+AB))$	$-B+A987-6-5+4^*(32-1)$
AA72	18806	$1-2-3+(-4^*5-(67-8^*9))^*A^*-B$	$BA98-7+65-4^*321$
AA73	18807	$-1^*2+(-3/-4^*-5+6)^*(7-8/9)+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+(-7-6^*5^*4)^*(-3-2)^*1$
AA74	18808	$123+4-(-56-78)^*9A-B$	$B-(-A987-65-4-32+1)$
AA75	18809	$-123-4-(-567-89)^*(A+B)$	$B-(-A987-65-4)-32^*-1$
AA76	18810	$-123^*(45-67-89-(-A-B))$	$B+A987+65-(-4-32)+1$
AA77	18811	$1^*2+(-3/-4^*-5+6)^*(7-8/9)+A-B$	$B+A987-6^*5^*-4+3-2^*1$
AA78	18812	$1+2+(-3^*-4^*5+6)^*(7-8/9)+A-B$	$-B-A98^*-7-65^*(43^*-2-1)$
AA79	18813	$-12+34^*5^*(67+8)+9AB$	$B+A987+(-6-5+4)^*-2+1$
AA7A	18814	$-12+3^*(4567-8-9AB)$	$BA98-7^*-6-54^*(3+21)$
AA7B	18815	$-12+34^*(-567+89A)-B$	$B+A987+65-(-43+2+1)$
AA80	18816	$12^*(-3+4+5+6-(-89A+B))$	$-B+A987+(6-5)^*4^*(-32+1)$
AA81	18817	$12-3^*-45+67^*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987-65^*4+321$
AA82	18818	$(-1-2^*(3-4^*5)+6^*7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8^*7+6^*5^*(4^*3/2-1)$
AA83	18819	$-1^*-23^*(4+567-89+A-B)$	$B+A987+65+4+3+2-1$
AA84	18820	$(1-(2-3-4)^*5)^*6+7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+65+4^*-321$
AA85	18821	$-1-2^*-34^*-5-6-78^*(-9-A)^*B$	$B+A987+65-(-43-2)+1$
AA86	18822	$((1-2^*3)^*4-(5-6^*-7))^*8-9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5+4^*3+2+1$
AA87	18823	$(-1-2^*3)^*(4-5^*6)^*(7+8^*9)+A+B$	$B-(-A987+6)-(-5-4-3^*21)$
AA88	18824	$-1+23-45^*6^*7^*-8+9^*-A^*-B$	$-B+A987-(-65-4+3^*-21)$
AA89	18825	$-1-2-3^*(-4567+8+9AB)$	$B+A987+(6+5+4)^*2+1$
AA8A	18826	$-1+((-2+3^*4)^*-5^*6^*-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6+5^*(-43+21))$
AA8B	18827	$123-45^*(-6-(-78+9A))^*B$	$-B+A987-(6^*5^*-4-32-1)$
AA90	18828	$1+2-3-456-(-7-8)^*-9A^*-B$	$B+A-9-8^*7^*(-6-5^*(4^*3+2))^*1$
AA91	18829	$1-(2-3-4)^*5^*6+7+8^*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-6+5+4^*3-21$
AA92	18830	$-12^*(-3+4)^*(5+67+8-9AB)$	$B+A987+(6+5+4)^*(3-2+1)$
AA93	18831	$((-1+2)^*3^*-4^*5+6)^*(7-8/9)+A+B$	$-B+A987-(-6-5)-4^*32^*-1$
AA94	18832	$-1^*2^*(34-5678+9+AB)$	$B+A987-6-5+4^*32+1$
AA95	18833	$-1-234-(56+78^*(-9-A)^*B)$	$B+A+(-9-(8-7))^*(-6-5^*4^*3)+2^*1$
AA96	18834	$1+23+4-(56+78)^*(-9-A^*B)$	$-B-A+(-9^*-8-7^*6)^*(5^*4+3+2^*-1)$
AA97	18835	$1234+567^*(8-9)^*(A-B)$	$B+A987-6-5+4^*(32+1)$
AA98	18836	$-1^*2^*(3456+7-89AB)$	$-B+A987-6^*(5+4-32+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
AA99	18837	$-12+34*(-567+89A)+B$	$B+A+9+8*7+6/5^{\wedge}(4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
AA9A	18838	$1*2-3*(-4^{\wedge}5*6+(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+65-4-3*-21$
AA9B	18839	$1^{\wedge}2-3*(-4^{\wedge}5*6+(-7-8)*9)-(A-B)$	$B-(-A987+65*4)+321$
AAA0	18840	$-1*-2*-3*-4*-5*(67-89-AB)$	$B+A-9*(8-7*-6*-5*(4+3*2)+1)$
AAA1	18841	$-1+2*(-3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)))*-9+A*B$	$-B-(-A987-6+54*-3)-21$
AAA2	18842	$-123+4*5*678-(9A-B)$	$BA-98+7*6*(-5-4+321)$
AAA3	18843	$1-(2+34*5)-67*(-89-AB)$	$BA9*(8-7)*(6+5)-4-(-3-2+1)$
AAA4	18844	$1*-2*(3+4)^{\wedge}(56+7-(-8+9AB))$	$-B+A987+6-5-(4+3)*-21$
AAA5	18845	$1-2*-3*4*(567-8)-(9+AB)$	$B+A987-6*(-54+32)-1$
AAA6	18846	$123+4*5-(-6-7)*8+9AB$	$-B+A987-6*-5+4*(32-1)$
AAA7	18847	$(-1-2)*(-3-4^{\wedge}5*6+(-7-8)*9)-(A-B)$	$B+A987+6*(54-32)+1$
AAA8	18848	$-1*(-2+345+6+7)*(-8-9-A-B)$	$-B+A987-6*(5+4-(32+1))$
AAA9	18849	$-1-(2-3-4)^{\wedge}5*6+7+8*9+A+B$	$B+A987+6+5+4*(32-1)$
AAAA	18850	$(1^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}3+4)^{\wedge}5*6+7+8*9+A+B$	$-B+A987-6*-5+4*-32*-1$
AAAB	18851	$-1+234*(5+6)-(7-89AB)$	$-B+A987-6-(-54*3+2+1)$
AA00	18852	$-1+2+34*(-567+89A)+B$	$B+A-9-(-8-7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4/(3/2-1))$
AA01	18853	$-1+2*(-34+5678-9A-B)$	$B+A987-(-6-5-4*32*1)$
AA02	18854	$1+23*456+78+9AB$	$-B*(A-987-6-54*(3+2)+1)$
AA03	18855	$-1-2-345*-6*7-8*-9*(-A-B)$	$-B-(-A987+6+54*-3-2+1)$
AA04	18856	$(-1+(-2*-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6+7)))^8*9-(A-B)$	$-B-A+(9*-8+7+6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3-(2+1)$
AA05	18857	$1-2-3*(-4^{\wedge}5*6+(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8)/-7*(6^{\wedge}5-4*(3+2^{\wedge}1))$
AA06	18858	$12*(-3+4-(-5-6)-(-78-9AB))$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7*-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-(2+1)$
AA07	18859	$1^{\wedge}2-3*(-4^{\wedge}5*6+(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	$B+A+(-9*-8-7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2/1$
AA08	18860	$(-1-(-2-3)^{\wedge}4)*-5*6+7+8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(9^{\wedge}(8-7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1$
AA09	18861	$-1+(-2-3*4*5)*(6*7+8)*9-A*B$	$B+A+9*(8+(7*6+5-4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
AA0A	18862	$-1+(-2*-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6+7))^8*9+A-B$	$BA+9*8^{\wedge}(7+6)*(5+4*3+2+1)$
AA0B	18863	$-12-3+4-56*(-78+9A)*-B$	$B+A987+6-54*-3-21$
AB00	18864	$-1*-2*(-3456+7+89AB)$	$BA98-(765+432)-1$
AB01	18865	$-1*(-23-4+56)*-7*(-8-9+A)*-B$	$BA98-765+432*-1$
AB02	18866	$1+(-2*-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6+7))^8*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-765-432+1$
AB03	18867	$-1+2*(-34+5678+9-AB)$	$-B-(-A987-6)+54*3+2-1$
AB04	18868	$123+45+67*(89+AB)$	$-B+A987+6-54*-3+2*1$
AB05	18869	$1-2*(34-5678-(9-AB))$	$-B+A987+6+54*3+2+1$
AB06	18870	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3*-4+5)*(6-7*-8*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9-(-8-7)*(-6-5^{\wedge}4+3)*-2*1$
AB07	18871	$1-(2-3^{\wedge}4+5)-6*(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-BA-9-87-(-6+543)*-21$
AB08	18872	$1+2-3-4-56*(-78+9A)*-B$	$-B-A+(-9+8*7)*-6*(-5-4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
AB09	18873	$-1*-23*(4+567-(89+A-B))$	$B+A+(-9-8)/-7*(6^{\wedge}5-(4+3^{\wedge}2))-1$
AB0A	18874	$-1-2*(-3-(4+5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)))^9+A-B$	$-BA+98+76*5*(4-32*-1)$
AB0B	18875	$-1+2*3456+7*8*(9A+B)$	$B+A987-(6-54*3+2)+1$
AB10	18876	$-1*-2*3*(-45+67)*(-8-(-9A-B))$	$B+A987+(-6-(5+43))*(-2-1)$
AB11	18877	$-1+2+3*(4567+8-9AB)$	$B+A-9+(8+7*6+5)/(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
AB12	18878	$1*-2*(-3+4+5-6-7-8*-9*-AB)$	$-B+A987-6*-5*(4+3)*(2-1)$
AB13	18879	$1+2-3*(-4567-8+9AB)$	$-B-(-A987+6+54*-3-21)$
AB14	18880	$-1-2+3+4-56*(-78+9A)*-B$	$-B-A+(-9*-8-7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1$
AB15	18881	$(-1-2+((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7)/8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+98-7*(65-4)*(-32+1)$
AB16	18882	$1-2+3+4-(-5+67)*(-89-AB)$	$-B-A9-87-(-6+543)*-21$
AB17	18883	$-1+(-2+3+4)^{\wedge}5*6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*5*(-4-32)-1$
AB18	18884	$1*2*(-345-6-7*(8-9AB))$	$-B+A987+6+5*(4+32)*1$
AB19	18885	$1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4*-5*6+(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+(-6-5)*4*-32*-1$
AB1A	18886	$-1-2*(34-5678+9A)+B$	$BA*(-9-(-87+6)-(5-43-(-2+1)))$
AB1B	18887	$-1+(-2-((3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/-8)*9-(A+B)$	$-B-A+9-8+7*(65-4)*(-32-1)$
AB20	18888	$(-1-((-2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*6+7))^8*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-7+6-(54+3)*21$
AB21	18889	$-1+(-2-((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6+54*-3)-(-2+1)$
AB22	18890	$12-3*(-4567-8+9AB)$	$B+A987+6+54*3+2*1$
AB23	18891	$1-(-2-((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7)/-8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-54*-3+21$
AB24	18892	$(1-(2-3-4)^{\wedge}5)*6-(-7-8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+(9*-8-7+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3/2)+1$
AB25	18893	$-1-2+3*(4-56)*(-78-9)+A*B$	$-B+A987-(-65+4*(-32+1))$
AB26	18894	$-1-2-3-(4-567-89)*(A+B)$	$B+A+9*((-8-7)*6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2^{\wedge}1-1))$
AB27	18895	$1-((-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5*-6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8-76*5*(-4-32)-1$
AB28	18896	$-1*(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5*-6+7)*8-9-(A-B)$	$B+A-((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
AB29	18897	$(-1-(2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5)*6-7*-8*9-(A+B)$	$-B+A987+65-4*32*-1$
AB2A	18898	$-1*-2*(-34+5678-9A)+B$	$-B*(-A98-7+6*(54-32))+1$
AB2B	18899	$(1*2+3)/4*5*6*7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8-7*6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3-2*1$
AB30	18900	$12*(34+56+789+AB)$	$B+A987+(-6-54)*3*(-2+1)$
AB31	18901	$-1+2+(34-5)*(-6*-78+9-(A+B))$	$B-(-A987+6+54*-3-21)$
AB32	18902	$((1+2*3)^{\wedge}4+5-6*7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9*-8+7+6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3+2-1$
AB33	18903	$(-1-2+((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7)/8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9-8-7*6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3+2/1$
AB34	18904	$(-1-((-2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*6+7))^8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9*-8+7+6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3+2+1$
AB35	18905	$-1-(2+((3+4)^{\wedge}5-(6-7))/-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)/(-7*6^{\wedge}5)+4/(3*-2-1)$
AB36	18906	$-12+3+45+6*(-7-8-9)*-AB$	$B+A987-6*(-54+3+21)$
AB37	18907	$12-3*-45*(6+7+89)+AB$	$-B-(-A987+6-5*(-43+2)*-1)$
AB38	18908	$-1*(2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7)/-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)/7*(-6^{\wedge}5+4-3-2)^{\wedge}1$
AB39	18909	$1-2+34*(-56+7)*-8-(-9-(A+B))$	$B+A+(-9-8)/-7*(6^{\wedge}5-(4-3-2))+1$
AB3A	18910	$-1*-2*(-34+5678-(-9*-A+B))$	$B-A*(-9-87-65)^{\wedge}(-4*-3-2)-1$
AB3B	18911	$1+2-((3+4)^{\wedge}5-(6-7))/-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(6+5)*-4*(3+2)+1$
AB40	18912	$-1-2+345*(6+7-89+AB)$	$B+A-9*(-8-7*-6*-5/-4*(3+2)+1)$
AB41	18913	$1-((-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5*-6+7)*8+9+A-B$	$B+A987-65+4*-3*-21$
AB42	18914	$1*2*(-3+4-(-5678+9-AB))$	$B+A987-6-5*-43-21$
AB43	18915	$(-1-((-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5+6))*(-7*8+9)+A+B$	$B+A987+65-4*(-32+1)$
AB44	18916	$-1*(-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5*-6+7)*8-9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*-6*(-5-4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
AB45	18917	$(-1-(2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5)*6-7*-8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*(4-321)$
AB46	18918	$1+2+3*4^{\wedge}5*6+7*8*9-(A+B)$	$B+A987+65+4*32-1$
AB47	18919	$1+2+3+4+56*(-78+9A)*B$	$-B+A987-6-5*-43+2*1$
AB48	18920	$((1+2*3)^{\wedge}4+5-6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$-B*-A*(-9-(87-(65-43)))*-2*1$
AB49	18921	$-12-345*-6*7-8-9AB$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*(5/4+3+2)^{\wedge}1$
AB4A	18922	$1/2-((3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6+54)*(-3-2+1)$
AB4B	18923	$(-1-2+(-3-4)*5)*(6-7*8*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+65*4+3*-21$
AB50	18924	$1+(-2-3*-4^{\wedge}5)*6-7*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)/-7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(-3/-2))-1$
AB51	18925	$-1-(-2+((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987+(65+43)*2+1$
AB52	18926	$(-1-2)*(3-4^{\wedge}5*6)-7*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-6+5*-43+21)$
AB53	18927	$1+(-2+((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6+7)/-8)*-9+A-B$	$-BA-98-76+543*21$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
AB54	18928	$-12 * (-3 - 4 - (-56 + 7)) * (89 - AB)$	$B + A - 9 - 8 * (7 \wedge (6 - 5 + 4) + 3 \wedge - 2) - 1$
AB55	18929	$-1 - 234 + 5 * 6 + 7 * 8 * (-9 - A) * B$	$-B + A - 9 - 8 * 7 * 6 - 543 * - 21$
AB56	18930	$-1 * (2 + (3 + 4) \wedge 5 + 6 - 7) / - 8 * 9 + A + B$	$-B + A987 + 6 - 54 * (-3 - 2 + 1)$
AB57	18931	$-12345 - 6 * 7 * 8 * (-9 * A + B)$	$BA98 - 76 - (-543 * - 2 + 1)$
AB58	18932	$1 * 2 * (3 - 4 - (-5678 + 9A + B))$	$BA98 - 76 + 543 * - 2 * 1$
AB59	18933	$-1 * 2 + 3 * 4 \wedge 5 * 6 + 7 * 8 * 9 + A - B$	$BA98 - 76 + 543 * - 2 + 1$
AB5A	18934	$-1 * - 2 * (3 - 4) * (-5678 + 9A + B)$	$-B - A + 9 - 8 * (-7 - 6 * 5) * 4 \wedge 3 + 2 \wedge 1$
AB5B	18935	$-123 + 45 * 6 * 7 * 8 - 9A * - B$	$-B - A + 9 - 8 * (-7 - 6 * 5) * 4 \wedge 3 + 2 + 1$
AB60	18936	$-1 * 2 * (3 - (4 - (-5678 + 9A) - B))$	$B + A987 - 6 + (5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$
AB61	18937	$-12 - 345 * - 6 * 7 - (-8 + 9A + B)$	$-B + A98 * (7 + 6) - 5 - 43 * 21$
AB62	18938	$1 + 23 + 45 * - 6 - 7 * 8 * (9 + A) * - B$	$-B + A987 + 65 * 4 - 32 * 1$
AB63	18939	$-123 + 4 * - 5 * - 678 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 * - 43 * (2 - 1)$
AB64	18940	$-123 + 4 * 5 * 678 + 9 * (A - B)$	$B + A - 9 - 8 * (7 \wedge (6 - 5 + 4) + 3 \wedge 2) + 1$
AB65	18941	$-1 - (2 + 34) - (-567 - 89) * (A + B)$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 4) \wedge 3) / 2 \wedge - 1$
AB66	18942	$12 * (-3 + 4) * (5 - 6 * - 7 + 8 + 9A * B)$	$-B + A987 - 6 - 5 * - 43 + 21$
AB67	18943	$1 - 2 - 34 + (567 + 89) * (A + B)$	$-B + A987 + 6 * (-5 + 43) - 2 + 1$
AB68	18944	$((1 - 2 \wedge 3) \wedge 4 - (-5 + 6 * 7) * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$-B + A987 - 6 * (-5 - (4 + 32 - 1))$
AB69	18945	$(-1 - 2 + (-3 - 4) * 5) * (6 - 7 * 8 * 9) + A + B$	$-B - A + (9 - 8 * 7 * 6) / (-5 * 4 * 3 + 2) \wedge - 1$
AB6A	18946	$-1 * - 2 * (3 - 4 + 5678 + 9 - AB)$	$B + A987 + 6 - 5 * (-43 + 2 - 1)$
AB6B	18947	$-1 * (-2 - 3 * 4 \wedge 5) * 6 - 7 * - 8 * 9 + A - B$	$BA98 - 7 * - 65 * (4 - 3 + 2) * - 1$
AB70	18948	$1 * 2 * (-3 + 4) * (5678 + 9 - AB)$	$B + A987 + 6 - (-5 * 43 + 2 + 1)$
AB71	18949	$12 - 345 * 6 * - 7 - 8 - 9AB$	$B - (A - 9 - 8 * - 7 * 6 + 543 * - 21)$
AB72	18950	$1 * - 2 * (3 - 4 - 5678 - 9 + AB)$	$BA - 98 * 76 + 54 * 321$
AB73	18951	$(-1 - (-2 + 3 \wedge 4) * - 5 * 6) * (7 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$-B - A + 9 * 8 + 7 * 6 * 5 * (4 - 32 * - 1)$
AB74	18952	$(-1 * 2 \wedge 3) \wedge 4 * (-5 + 6 * 7) / 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 * - 8 - 7 * 6) * (5 \wedge 4 + 3 * 2) + 1$
AB75	18953	$(1 \wedge 2 - (3 + 4) \wedge 5 + 6 * - 7) / - 8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + 7) * (-6 - 5 \wedge 4) * 3 + 2 \wedge 1$
AB76	18954	$1 * - 2 * (34 - 5678 + 9 * A - B)$	$-B + A987 + 6 - (5 * - 43 - 21)$
AB77	18955	$-1 * 2 + 3 * 4 \wedge 5 * 6 + 7 * 8 * 9 + A + B$	$BA9 - 8 * - 7 * 65 * 4 + 3 * - 2 * 1$
AB78	18956	$-1 * - 2 * (3 + 4) * (56 - (-7 - 89A) + B)$	$B + A - 9 - 8 * (7 * - 6 + 5) * 4 * 3 \wedge (2 - 1)$
AB79	18957	$1 + 2 * 34 + 56 * (-78 + 9A) * B$	$-BA + 9876 - 5 * (-4 - 321)$
AB7A	18958	$-1 + (-2 + 3 \wedge 4) * - 5 * - 6 * (7 - (8 - 9)) + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 * (-7 - 6 * 5) * 4 \wedge 3 + 2 / 1$
AB7B	18959	$-1 - 23 + 45 * 6 * - 7 * - 8 * 9 * AB$	$B + A - 9 - 8 * (7 * - 6 + 5) / 4 \wedge - 3 + 2 + 1$
AB80	18960	$1 * (-2 - 3 + 45) * 6 * 7 * (-89 + A * B)$	$B + A + 9 - (-8 - 7) * (-6 - 5 \wedge 4) * (-3 - (-2 + 1))$
AB81	18961	$1 - 23 - 45 * - 6 * 7 * 8 - 9 * - AB$	$B - (-A987 - 65 * 4 + 32 - 1)$
AB82	18962	$1 - 23 + 4 + (567 + 89) * (A + B)$	$BA9 + 8 * - 7 * - 65 * 4 * (3 - 2) + 1$
AB83	18963	$-12 - (3 + 4 * 5 * - 678) - 9 - AB$	$B + A + 9 - 8 + (-7 - 6) * ((-5 - 4) \wedge 3 * 2 + 1)$
AB84	18964	$-1 + (-2 - 3 * - 4 * 5) * (-6 * - 7 * 8 - 9) + A - B$	$B * (-A + 987 + 6 * 5 * 4 * 3 - 21)$
AB85	18965	$-1 * - 2 * (-3 * - 4 + 5 \wedge 6 / (7 + 8)) * 9 + A - B$	$-BA + 9876 - 543 * (-2 - 1)$
AB86	18966	$-1 + 234 - 5 - 67 * (-89 - AB)$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * ((7 * - 6 + 5) * 4 \wedge 3 + 2 - 1)$
AB87	18967	$1 + 23 - 4 * 5 * (-678 + 9) - (-A + B)$	$BA98 - 7 - 6 * 5 * (-43 - 2) * - 1$
AB88	18968	$1 + 23 - 4 * - 5 * (678 - 9) * (-A + B)$	$BA98 + 7 * 6 * (5 - 4) * 32 * - 1$
AB89	18969	$-1 - 2 - 3 * 4 + (-567 - 89) * (-A - B)$	$BA - 9 * 8 + 7 * 6 * 5 * (4 + 32) - 1$
AB8A	18970	$-12 * (-3 + 4) * (5 - 67 - 89A - B)$	$B + A987 - 65 * - 4 - 3 - 21$
AB8B	18971	$-12 - 3 + 4 + (-567 - 89) * (-A - B)$	$-BA - 9 * 8 - (76 + 543 * - 21)$
AB90	18972	$1 - 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5) * (-6 - 7 * 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * (-7 - 6 * 5) * 4 \wedge 3 - 2 \wedge 1$
AB91	18973	$-1 - 23 - 4 * 5 * - 678 - (9 + A * B)$	$-B + A987 - 65 * - 4 - 3 * (2 - 1)$
AB92	18974	$-12 - 3 + 4 * - 5 * - 678 - 9A - B$	$B - A9 * (-87 - (65 + 4 - 32 + 1))$
AB93	18975	$(1 \wedge 2 - (3 + 4) \wedge 5 + 6 * - 7) / - 8 * 9 + A + B$	$-B + A987 - 65 * 4 * (-3 - 2) - 1$
AB94	18976	$-1 + 234 - (-5 + 67 * - 89 - AB)$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 * - 3 - 21$
AB95	18977	$(-1 + 2 \wedge 3 * 4) * (-5 - 6) * - 7 * 8 - 9 - A * B$	$-B + A987 - 6 * - 54 - 3 * 21$
AB96	18978	$-1 * 2 * (-3 + 4) * (-5678 - (-9A + B))$	$-B + A987 + 65 * 4 + 3 - (2 - 1)$
AB97	18979	$(-1 - (-2 * (3 + 4 \wedge 5 + 6) - 7 * 8)) * 9 - A * B$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 - 4 * - 3 * 21$
AB98	18980	$1 * 2 * (-3 + 4 + 5678 - 9A + B)$	$-B + A + 9 - 7 * 65 * (4 - 32 - 1)$
AB99	18981	$-12 - 3 + 4 * - 5 * - 678 - (-9 + AB)$	$-B + A987 - 6 + 54 * (3 + 2) - 1$
AB9A	18982	$((1 + 2 + 3) \wedge 4 - 5 * 6) * (7 + 8) - 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A987 + (65 - 4) * (3 - (-2 + 1))$
AB9B	18983	$(-1 - (2 - 3 * (4 \wedge 5 - 6))) * - 7 * - 8 / 9 + A - B$	$-B * - A + 9 * ((-8 - 7) * 6 + (5 + 4) \wedge (3 + 2 \wedge - 1))$
ABA0	18984	$1 + 2 * (-34 + 5678) - (9A + B)$	$BA9 - 8 - 76 * 54 * - 3 - 2 + 1$
ABA1	18985	$-1 - 2 * (-3 - (4 + 5 \wedge 6 / (7 + 8))) * 9 + A * B$	$-BA + 9 + 8 + 7 * (6 + 54) * (32 + 1)$
ABA2	18986	$-1 + (-2 - 3 * - 4 * 5) * (-6 * - 7 * 8 - 9) + A + B$	$-B - A9 + 8 - 7 - (-6 + 543) * - 21$
ABA3	18987	$-12 + 3 - 4 * 5 * - 678 + 9 - AB$	$BA9 - 8 + 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 * - 3 - 2 * - 1$
ABA4	18988	$1 * 2 * (3 - 4 + 5678 - 9 * A - B)$	$B + A + ((-9 * - 8 + 7) * - 6 * 5 * - 4 + 3) * 2 + 1$
ABA5	18989	$-1 + 2 - 3 - 4 * 5 * - 678 - 9A - B$	$B + A987 - 6 + 5 + 4 * - 3 * - 21$
ABA6	18990	$-1 + 2 * 3456 - 7 * 89 * - A - B$	$B + A + 9 - 8 * ((-7 - 6 * 5) * 4 \wedge 3 - 2 \wedge 1)$
ABA7	18991	$1 - 2 * (34 - 5678) + 9 - AB$	$B + A987 + 6 - 5 - 4 * - 3 * 21$
ABA8	18992	$1 * 2 * (-3 + 4 - (-5678 - 9 - A * - B))$	$B - A9 - (8 + 7 + (6 - 543) * 21)$
ABA9	18993	$12 - 345 - (6 - (-7 - 8) * 9A * - B)$	$B + A + 9 + 8 - (-7 - 6) * (5 + 4) \wedge 3 * 2 + 1$
ABAA	18994	$1 - 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5) * (-6 - 7 * 8) * 9 + A + B$	$BA9 + 8 * - 7 * 6 * (5 + 4 + 3) * - 2 + 1$
ABAB	18995	$-1 + 2 - (-3 - 4 * 5 * 678 - (9A - B))$	$-B - A - (-9 - (-8 + 7 + (-6 - 5) * (-4 * 3) \wedge (2 + 1)))$
ABB0	18996	$(1 + 2 * 3 + 4) * 5 * (6 * 7 * 8 + 9) + A + B$	$B + A987 + 65 * 4 - (3 - 2 + 1)$
ABB1	18997	$(-1 - (-2 * 3) \wedge 4 + 5 * 6) * (-7 - 8) - 9 - (A - B)$	$-B * (-A - 9 - 8 - 765 - (432 + 1))$
ABB2	18998	$1 + 2 * (3 + 4 + 5678) - (-9 - A) * - B$	$-B - (-A987 + 6 * - 5) + 4 * - 3 * - 21$
ABB3	18999	$12345 - 67 * 8 * 9 - A * B$	$B + A987 - 6 * - 54 - 3 * 21$
ABB4	19000	$-1 * (2 + 3) * 4 * - 5 - (678 + (9 - A) * B))$	$BA9 + 8 + 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 * - 3 - 2 + 1$
ABB5	19001	$1 - 2 + 3 * 4 * (56 - 7) * 8 - 9 + AB$	$BA9 + 8 - 7 * 6 * 5 * 4 * - 3 * (2 - 1)$
ABB6	19002	$((1 + 2 + 3) \wedge 4 - 5 * 6) * (7 + 8) - 9 + A + B$	$B + A - 9 * (-8 * - 7 + 6 - 5) * (-4 / 3 \wedge - 2 - 1)$
ABB7	19003	$1 + ((-2 * - 3) \wedge 4 - 5 * 6) * (7 + 8) - 9 + A + B$	$-B - A + 9 * 8 * 7 * 6 + (5 * 4) \wedge 3 * 2 \wedge 1$
ABB8	19004	$1 * 2 * (3 - (-4 - 5678) - (-9 + A * B))$	$B + A987 + 65 * 4 - (-3 - 2) + 1$
ABB9	19005	$(-1 - (2 - 3 * (4 \wedge 5 - 6))) * - 7 * - 8 / 9 + A + B$	$-B - (-A987 + 6 * - 5 * - 4 - 321)$
ABBA	19006	$-1 - (-23 - 4 * 5 * 678 + 9) - AB$	$-B + A987 + 6 * (5 + 43) + 2 * 1$
ABBB	19007	$-1 + 2 * (-345 + 67 + 89A) * B$	$-B + A + 9 * 8 * (7 + 6 - 5 + 4 \wedge (3 + 2 - 1))$
B000	19008	$1 * 2 * (345 - 67 - 89A) * - B$	$-B - A + 9 - (-8 - 7) * (-6 - (5 \wedge 4 + 3)) * - 2 * 1$
B001	19009	$-1 * 2 \wedge 3 * (-4 + 5 * 6 + 7) * - 8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA98 - 7 - 6 + 543 * - 2 * 1$
B002	19010	$1 - 2 \wedge 3 * (-4 + 5 * 6 + 7) * - 8 * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA98 - 7 - 6 - 543 * 2 + 1$
B003	19011	$(-1 - 2) * (-3 - 4 \wedge 5) * 6 - 7 * - 8 * 9 + A + B$	$BA98 + 7 - 6 * 5 * (-43 - 2 + 1)$
B004	19012	$-12 * (-34 - 56 + 7 - (89A - B))$	$-B + A + 9 * 8 + (-7 - 6) * ((-5 - 4) \wedge 3 * 2 + 1)$
B005	19013	$-1 + 23 * 456 - 7 * - 8 * (9 - (-A - B))$	$BA - 9 - 8 * (-765 + 43 * - 21)$
B006	19014	$-1 * 2 * (-34 - 5678 - (-9A - B))$	$-B + A987 - (-65 * 4 - 32 * 1)$
B007	19015	$(-1 / -2 + 3 * 4) * - 5 * (6 * 7 + 8) * 9 - A * B$	$-B + A987 + 65 * 4 + 32 + 1$
B008	19016	$-1 - 2 + (-3 - 4) * (5 + 6) * (-7 - 8 * (9 + A + B))$	$-BA - (98 + 7 - 6 - 543 * 21)$
B009	19017	$(-1 - (-2 * 3) \wedge 4 + 5 * 6) * (-7 - 8) - 9 + A + B$	$-BA + 98 * (-7 + 6) + 543 * 21$
B00A	19018	$(-1 + (-2 + 3 \wedge 4) * 5 * 6 + 7) * 8 + 9 - (A - B)$	$BA98 - 765 - 4 - 321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B00B	19019	-123-4*5*(678+9)-A*B	-B*(A+9)*(-87-6+5-4*3+21)
B010	19020	1*2*(-3-4-(-5678-9*-A)+B)	-BA+9876-54*(-32+1)
B011	19021	1+((-2*-3)^4-5*6)*(7+8)+9+A+B	BA98-7+6-543*2*1
B012	19022	(-1-(-2-3*(-4-5)*6)*-7)*(8+9)+A-B	BA98+7*-6-5*-4*3*-21
B013	19023	1+2+3*4*(56-(-78-9AB))	BA98+7-6-543*-2*-1
B014	19024	1*-234*(-5-67-(89-AB))	BA98+7-6-543*2+1
B015	19025	1+((-2+3^4)*-5*-6+7)*8+9+A-B	-B-A+(9-8)^7+(-6*(5*4+3))^2+1
B016	19026	-12-34*(-5+678-9AB)	BA98-765+4-321
B017	19027	-1+2*(34+5678-(-9+AB))	-BA-9-87+6-543*-21
B018	19028	-1*-2*(34+5678+9-AB)	BA*(-9+8-(-76+5-43+2-1))
B019	19029	1+2*34*56-7-89*-AB	B+A+9*8*(7+6-5+4^(3+2-1))
B01A	19030	12+3-(4*5*-678-(-9A+B))	-B+A987-6*-54-(-3+21)
B01B	19031	(1+(2^3+4)^5)*(6+7)^(8-9)-A*B	BA98+7+65*4*(3*-2+1)
B020	19032	12+3*(-4-56)-78*(9+A)*-B	B+A987+6*(54+3*-2-1)
B021	19033	((1-2^3)^4-(-5+6)*7)*8-9-A*B	-BA+9-87-6-543*-21
B022	19034	12+3*4*(56+78+9AB)	BA98+7+6+543*-2-1
B023	19035	-1*23*(-45+6)*(-78+9A-B)	BA98+7+6*54*(3+2-1)
B024	19036	123-4+5-6*(-7-8-9)*AB	BA98+7+6+543*-2+1
B025	19037	-1*(-2-3)^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9-(A+B)	-B-A9-8-(76+543*-21)
B026	19038	1-2*(3+(-4^5-6*7+8)*9)+A-B	-B-A9-87+6-543*-21
B027	19039	1-2+34*(5-678+9AB)	-BA-9*87+(-6-5)*4*-321
B028	19040	-12*34*(56-78-9-A+B)	B+A+(-9*-8-7*6)*(5^4+3^2)-1
B029	19041	-1+2-34*(-5+678-9AB)	B*(-A9-876-(-5-432+1))
B02A	19042	-1-((-2*-3)^4+5^6+7)/-8*9+A-B	-BA-9+8-76+543*21
B02B	19043	-12+3456-(78+9)*-AB	BA+9-8+76*5*(4-32*-1)
B030	19044	1-((-2*-3)^4+5^6+7)/-8*9+A-B	-B+A987-(65+4-321)
B031	19045	-1*((-2*-3)^4+5^6+7)/-8*9-(A-B)	-B+A987+65+4*-3*-21
B032	19046	1234+5+6*(89+A*B)	-B-(-A987-6*54)-(-3+2+1)
B033	19047	1+23-4*5*-678+9-A*B	-B+A987-6*-54-3-2*1
B034	19048	(1+(2^3+4)^5)/(6+7)-8*9-(A+B)	B-A9-87-6-543*-21
B035	19049	-1*-2*(3-(-4^5-6*7+8)*9)+A-B	-B-A(-9-8+7)*(-6*(-5/4^3+2)-1)
B036	19050	-12-345*6*-7-8+9A*-B	B+A+9-(-8-7)*(-6-(5^4+3))*-2*1
B037	19051	((1-2^3)^4-(-5+6)*7)*8+9-A*B	-B+A987+65*4+3*21
B038	19052	-1*2*(34-5678+9-(-A-B))	B+A987-(-6*54-(3-21))
B039	19053	NA	-B-(-A987+6*54)-(-3-2*-1)
B03A	19054	-12*(34-(56-78)-9AB)	-B-A+(9*-8+7-6*5^4)*(-3-2)*1
B03B	19055	((1-2^3)^4-(-5+6*7)*8)*9+A*B	-B+A987-6-54+321
B040	19056	-1*2*3*(4*-567+8-9-(A+B))	BA98-7*(65-4)*3+21
B041	19057	-1*(-2-3)^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A-B	BA98-(7-6*5*(-43-(-2+1)))
B042	19058	1*2*(34+5678-9A+B)	-B+A+9876+5*(-4+321)
B043	19059	1-2*(-34-5678-(-9A+B))	-B+A987+6+54*3*2+1
B044	19060	-12+3+4*-5*(-678+9)+AB	-BA+9+8-76-543*-21
B045	19061	12-(3+4*-5*(678-9)+A*-B)	-B+A987+6*54+3*(2+1)
B046	19062	-1*23*(-45+6*-78-9A*-B)	-BA-9-8*7-6-543*-21
B047	19063	(-1-(-2-(-3*4^5+6)*-7)*8/9+A-B)	-B*(A9-(876+5+432)-1)
B048	19064	-123-45*-6*-7*-8+9AB	BA98-7*-6+543*2*-1
B049	19065	-1*((-2*-3)^4+5^6+7)/-8*9+A+B	BA98+7*6-543*2+1
B04A	19066	1-((-2*-3)^4+5^6+7)/-8*9+A+B	B+A987-65-(4-321)
B04B	19067	1*(-23+4)*(5-678-(9-AB))	-B+A987+6-54+321
B050	19068	-12*(3+45-(6-7-8)-9AB)	-B-(-A+98+76)+543*21
B051	19069	-1+2*(34+5678+9*-A-B)	B+A-9*-8*(7+6*5)+4^(3*2+1)
B052	19070	-1-2^3(3+4)*(-5-6)*7-8*9+A-B	B-A-98-76+543*21
B053	19071	-123-4*5*-678-(9-AB)	B+A+(-9*-8-7*6)*(5^4+3^2+1)
B054	19072	1+2^3(3+4)*(5+6)*7+8*9+A-B	BA9-8*-765*(-4+3)*-2-1
B055	19073	-1*-2^3(3+4)*(5-6*(-7-8-9))-(-A-B)	B+A987+65*4-3*-21
B056	19074	-1*(23-4*5*6*-7)*(8-9-A-B)	B-(-A987+65-4-321)
B057	19075	1^2*3^3(4+5)+6-7*8*9-A*B	B+A987-6*-54+3-2*1
B058	19076	(-1-(2+(-3*4^5+6)*7*8))/9+A-B	B+A987+65*(4+3-2)+1
B059	19077	-1*-2*(3-4^5-6*7+8)*9-(A+B)	B+A987-6-54+321
B05A	19078	(-1-(-2+(-3*4^5+6)*7)*8)/9+A-B	-B-A-(-9876+5*(-4-321))
B05B	19079	-1+2*(3+4-5-678)*(-9+A-B)	B-(-A987-6)-(-54*3*2+1)
B060	19080	1*-2*-3*45*(-6-7*-8+9-A+B)	-B-(-A987-6*54-3)+21
B061	19081	-1-23-4*5*-678*(-9+A)-B	-B+A9*(8+7*(6-(54-32)))*-1
B062	19082	12*(3+4-56-7-(-8-9AB))	-B*-A+9+8-(-7-6)*(5+4)^3*2+1
B063	19083	-1*(-2*(-3+4^5+6*7)+8)*9+A+B	-BA+9876-54*-32-1
B064	19084	1-23-4*5*-678-9A+B	-BA+9876-54*-32*1
B065	19085	(-1-(-2-(-3*4^5+6)*-7)*8/9+A+B)	-BA+9876-54*-32+1
B066	19086	1234-5*(67-89)*AB	B+A-9*(-8+7/6)*-5*(-4^3+2)*1
B067	19087	1-2^3*(-4^5-6^7+8)*9-(A+B)	B+A+98-(7+6-543)*21
B068	19088	12345-6*7*-8*-9-A-B	-B+A987-6*-5*(-4*-3-2*-1)
B069	19089	-123-456*(78-(-9+AB))	B-(-A987-(6-54+321))
B06A	19090	-123+4567+89*-A*-B	-B+A987+6*54-32*-1
B06B	19091	1*2+(3+4)^(5+6-7)*8-9-A*B	-B+A987+6*54+32+1
B070	19092	-1*2*(-34+5-67-8*-9*-AB)	BA98+7*6*5*(4+3)-2*1
B071	19093	-1*-2^3(3+4)*(5-6*(-7-8-9))+A+B	B+A*((-9-8-7)*6+5)*-4^3*-2^1
B072	19094	12-345*6*-7+8-9A*B	-B-A-9-8+7-(-6+543)*-21
B073	19095	-1/-2*(-3-4^5*6*7)*-8/9-A-B	-BA+9+87+(-6+543)*21
B074	19096	1*-2*(34-5678+9A+B)	B+A+(9*-8+7-6*5^4)*(-3-2)*1
B075	19097	-12+3+4*-5*6+78*(-9-A)*-B	B+A+(-9*-8-(7-6*5^4))*(3+2)+1
B076	19098	1-2*(-3-4^5-6*7+8)*9+A-B	B+A-9^(-8+7+6)+5^4(4+3)+2-1
B077	19099	-1-23+4567+8*9AB	-B-(-A987+6+5*4)+321
B078	19100	-1*(23-(4567-8*-9AB))	B+A-9^(-8+7+6)+5^4(4+3)+2+1
B079	19101	1-(23-4567)-8*-9AB	BA98+7-6*5*(43+2*-1)
B07A	19102	123-4*5*-678-9*(A+B)	B+A987-6*-54+3+21
B07B	19103	12+345*6*7-(89A+B)	-BA-9-8-(7+6-543*21)
B080	19104	(-1+2^3*4)*(-5-6)*-7*8+9+A-B	B+A-9-8*(-7-6*5)*(4^3+2^1-1)
B081	19105	1-23+4*5*-678*(9-A)+B	B*-A+9+8*7*(6+5-4)^3-2^1
B082	19106	1+2*-3-4*-5*678+9*(A-B)	-B+A+9876+543*(2+1)
B083	19107	1-2-3-4*5*-678-9*(-A+B)	-BA-98-(-76-543*21)
B084	19108	1+2+345*-6*-7+(89A)*-B	B+A-9-8*-7*((6+5-4)^3-2)/1
B085	19109	12345-6*7*8*-9*(A-B)	-B*-A+(-9*-8-(7+6))*(-5*-4^3+2)+1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B086	19110	-12-3+4567+8*9AB	-B+A987-6-5-4+321
B087	19111	1+2*-3*-456+7+89AB	-B+A987+6-5*4+321
B088	19112	-1+2345-67+89AB	BA98+76-543*2*1
B089	19113	-1*(-2345+67-89AB)	B+A987-6*-54+32+1
B08A	19114	1+2345-67+89AB	-B-(A9+8+7+6+543*-21)
B08B	19115	-12+345+67*(89+AB)	-BA-9*-8-76-543*-21
B090	19116	-12+3-(-4567+8*-9AB)	-B-A-9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3+2-1
B091	19117	(1-2+3^(4-5+6))*(7+8*9)+A-B	-BA-(9+8-7+6+543*-21)
B092	19118	-1*2*(3+4-(5678-9))-(-A-B))	-B+A987-6-5+4+321
B093	19119	-12-34-(567+8*9A)*-B	B+A+(-9*-8+(7+6)*(5+4)^3)/2^1-1
B094	19120	((1^2+3)^4*-5+6)*(-7-8)+9-(A-B)	-B+A987-(6-5+4)+321
B095	19121	-1-2-(3-4567+8*-9AB)	B+A987-(6-5*-4-321)
B096	19122	-1*(2+3-(4567-8*-9AB))	-B-(-A987-6+5+4-321)
B097	19123	1-2-3+4567+8*9AB	B-(A9-8)-(-7*-6+543*-21)
B098	19124	-12*(34+567-89*(A+B))	B+A987-6-5*-4*(-3+21)
B099	19125	1-2*(-3-4)-(-5-67*-8)*(-9-(A+B))	-B-A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4-3^2)+1
B09A	19126	-1*(-2+3-4567-8*9AB)	-B-A9-8-7+6+543*21
B09B	19127	-1*(2-345-67*(89+AB))	-B-A-9*8*7+(6*5+4)^3/2*1
B0A0	19128	1*2*(-34-(-5678-9))-(-A+B))	-B+A987-6-(-5-(4+321))
B0A1	19129	1-2-(-3-(4567+8*9AB))	-B+A987*(6-5)+4+321
B0A2	19130	1*2*(-34+5678+9*(-A+B))	-B+A987+6-5+4+321
B0A3	19131	-1+2+3+4567-8*-9AB	-B+A987+6+(5-4)*321
B0A4	19132	1*-2*(34-5678-9+A-B)	-B+A987+6+5-4+321
B0A5	19133	-1+(-2-3*(-4-5)*6*7)*(8+9)-A*B	-BA-9+8+7-6-543*-21
B0A6	19134	-1*(-23+4+5)*(678+9A-B)	B+A+9*-8-76-543*-21
B0A7	19135	1+(-2-3*(-4-5)*6*7)*(8+9)-A*B	-BA+9-8+7-6+543*21
B0A8	19136	-1*2*(34-5678+9-A-B)	B+A987+6+5*-4*(3-21)
B0A9	19137	-1/-2*(-3-4^5*6*7)*-8/9+A+B	-B-(A+98+7)-(-6+543*-21)
B0AA	19138	12-(3-4567+8*-9AB)	-B-A+98*(-7+6)+543*21
B0AB	19139	(1+(2^3+4)^5)/(6+7)+8-9+A-B	-B-(-A987-654+321)
B0B0	19140	-1*(2-3+4-567-8*9A)*B	-B*-A*(-9-(8+65*4)+3-21)
B0B1	19141	((1+2*3)^4-(5+6))*(7-(8-9))+A+B	-B-A+9876-54*(32+1)
B0B2	19142	((1-2^3)^4-(-5+6)*7)*8-9+A-B	B+A987-6+5-4+321
B0B3	19143	12+345+67*(89+AB)	BA98-7-6-54*(-3+21)
B0B4	19144	12+3+4567+8*9AB	-B-A9+8+7-6+543*21
B0B5	19145	1/-2*(-3-4^5*6)*-7*-8/9+A+B	-B*-A-9+(8+7+6*5*4+3)^2/1
B0B6	19146	1*-2*(-3-4-5678+9+A+B)	B+A+9*(8+(-7*6-5+4-3)^2+1)
B0B7	19147	-1+2+3^(4+5)+(-6-7*8)*9+A+B	-BA+9-8+7+6-543*-21
B0B8	19148	12+3-4*5*-678+(-9+A)*B	-B-A9-8-(7-6+543*-21)
B0B9	19149	-1+2345-(6*7-89AB)	B-(-A987-6*54)+3*21
B0BA	19150	1+2-3-4*5*-678+9+A+B	B-(-A987+6)-(-5-4-321)
B0BB	19151	-1*(-234+567+89A)*-B	B*(A9876-5*-4+3*21)
B100	19152	-123*-4*(-56+7+8-9*-A-B)	B+A987+6-5+4+321
B101	19153	-1+23+4567-8*-9AB	-B-A+(9+8*7)*(6+(5+4*3)^2)-1
B102	19154	-1-2*(-345-67)*(8+9)-A-B	B+A987-(-6-5)-4+321
B103	19155	1+23+4567-8*-9AB	BA98-7+6+54*(3-21)
B104	19156	1+2+(-3*4^5-6)*-7*8/9-(A-B)	B+A-9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2+1
B105	19157	(1+(2^3+4)^5)/(6+7)+8+9+A-B	-B-(-A+98+7)-(-6-543*21)
B106	19158	1*(-23-4)*(-567-8+9*(A+B))	BA-98+7+(6-543)*-21
B107	19159	123+4+(-567-89)*(-A-B)	BA-987-654*(3-21)
B108	19160	((1-2^3)^4-(-5+6)*7)*8+9+A-B	-BA-98-7+(6+543)*21
B109	19161	(1+(2^3+4)^5)/(6+7)+8-9+A+B	B+A987+654-321
B10A	19162	-1*(-2-3+4-56)*7(8-9A)*-B	B+A987+6+5+4+321
B10B	19163	-1-23*-456-(-7-8)*(-9+AB)	-BA+9-(-8-7)+6-543*-21
B110	19164	-1+2-3+4-56-78*(9+A)*-B	-B+A+98*(-76+5*43)+21
B111	19165	1^2+3^(4+5)+6-7*8*9-(A+B)	-B-A-(-9+8)-(76-543*21)
B112	19166	12*(3+456-7-8*-9*A+B)	B-(A9-8-(7-6))+543*21
B113	19167	-12+3456-(-789A+B)	-B+A-9-8-76-543*-21
B114	19168	-1*-2*(3-4)*(-5678-(9-A-B))	-B-(-A+9+87-6)+543*21
B115	19169	-1-2+3^(4+5)-6-7*8*9+A-B	B+A-9*8*7+(6*5+4)^3/2*1
B116	19170	-1*-2*(-3+456)*(-78-(-9A+B))	BA*(98-7-65+43*2+1)
B117	19171	1+23*-45*-6-7*-8*9*(A+B)	BA98-7-65*(-4-3+21)
B118	19172	1*-2*(-3+4)*(-5678+9-(A-B))	BA98-7-(654+321)
B119	19173	1+2*(-34+5678-(-9-A-B))	-B+A987-6+5*-43*-2+1
B11A	19174	1*-2*(3-4-5678+9-A+B)	B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4-3^2+1)
B11B	19175	-1-2-3-(45-6)-78*(9A)*-B	B+A-9*-8*7*-6*(5+4/3)*2/1
B120	19176	-1*-2*-3*4*-567+8-9-(A-B)	-BA+9-8-7*-6-543*-21
B121	19177	1+2+3^(4+5)-6-7*8*9-(A-B)	-B-A-9+8*(7+6*5+4*3)^2-1
B122	19178	-1-2+3456+789A-B	B-A9-(-8-7-6-543*21)
B123	19179	1*2345-6-7+89AB	B+A-(98-(-7+6)+543*-21)
B124	19180	1-(-2345+6)-(-7-89AB)	BA+9*-8-7*(-6-54)^2(32+1)
B125	19181	-1-2+3^(4+5)+6-7*8*9+A-B	B+A987+6*5-(-4-321)
B126	19182	-1+2+3456+789A-B	B+A+9-8*7*6*(5-4^3+2)^1
B127	19183	-1*(-2-3456-789A+B)	-B+A987-6+54+321
B128	19184	1+2+3456+789A-B	-B+A987+6-5*43*2*-1
B129	19185	-12-3+4*-5-6-78*(-9-A)*B	BA9+8*(-7-65)*(-43+21)
B12A	19186	1^2+3^(4+5)+6-7*8*9+A-B	BA98+7-(654+321)
B12B	19187	1+2+3^(4+5)+6-7*8*9+A-B	B-(A-9+8+7+6+543*-21)
B130	19188	1-(-2*(-3+4^5)-6*(7+8))*9+A-B	BA-9+8*7*(6-5+4)*(32-1)
B131	19189	-12+3456+789A+B	B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4-3*2)-1
B132	19190	1-2*3+(456+789-A)*B	B+A-9-87-(-6-543*21)
B133	19191	-1+2345*(-6+7)+89AB	B+A+(9*8+7+6+5^4)*3^1(2+1)
B134	19192	1+2345-(-6-(-7+89AB))	B+A+9*(-8*-7*6+(5+4)^3)*2+1
B135	19193	1*2345-6+7+89AB	B-(-A987+6-5*-43*-2)-1
B136	19194	1+2345-(6-7)+89AB	BA98-76-5-43*21
B137	19195	12-(-3456-789A+B)	-B+A987+6+54+321
B138	19196	-1-2*345*-6-(-789A-B)	B-(-A-9-(-87-6)-543*21)
B139	19197	-1*23*(4+5)*-67+8-(9+A)+B	B+A+(9+8*7)*(6+(5-4*3)^2)+1
B13A	19198	1*2*(-3-(-4-5678-9))-A+B	-B-(-A987-(65-4)-321)
B13B	19199	-1-2*34*5*(67-8-9+A*-B)	B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4-(3+2))+1
B140	19200	-1-(2-3456-(789A+B))	-B+A987+(6+5*-4)*32*-1

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B141	19201	$-1*(2-3456-789A-B)$	$-B+A+9+8-76+543*21$
B142	19202	$1-2+3456+789A+B$	$BA-9*8+7+(-6+543)*21$
B143	19203	$1+2+(3+4)^(5+6-7)*8-9-(A-B)$	$-B-(-A-9*-8)-(-7+6)+543*21$
B144	19204	$-1+2-(-3456-789A-B)$	$-B-(-A987+65)-(-432+1)$
B145	19205	$1*2+3456+789A+B$	$B+A987-6+54+321$
B146	19206	$1-(-2-3456-(789A+B))$	$-BA-9-(8-(76+543*21))$
B147	19207	$-1-23-(-45*6*7*8-9AB)$	$B-A9-8*-7-6+543*21$
B148	19208	$-12*(-3-(-45-6-7+8+9AB))$	$B+A+9-87+6+543*21$
B149	19209	$1^2+3^4(4+5)-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2-1$
B14A	19210	$1*-2*(3-4-5678-9-A+B)$	$B+A-9-8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2/1$
B14B	19211	$1+2+3^4(4+5)-6*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$BA-(98+76-543*21)$
B150	19212	$-1*-2*(3-4+5678*(9-A)+B)$	$B+A-9-8-7*(6-5*4)^3/(2-1)$
B151	19213	$-1-2+(3+4)^(5+6-7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+76*5*(4-3+2)-1$
B152	19214	$1*-2*(-3+4-(5678-9-(A-B)))$	$BA98-76*(5+4+3*2*1)$
B153	19215	$1*2^4(3*4)+5*6*7*8*9+A-B$	$-B+A-9*8+7+6+543*21$
B154	19216	$1+2+34-(5+6)*(7+8+9)*(A+B)$	$B+A+9-8-7*((6-5*4)^3+2)/1$
B155	19217	$12+3456+789A+B$	$B+A987-(-6-54-321)$
B156	19218	$-1*2*(3-4-5678+9-A-B)$	$-BA-9*8-(-7-6)+543*21$
B157	19219	$1+2+(3+4)^(5+6-7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+65-43*-21)$
B158	19220	$-1*(23+4)*5678-9AB$	$BA-98-7*-6*(-5+4)*-321$
B159	19221	$1^2+3^4(4+5)^(5+6-7)*8-9+A+B$	$-BA-9+87-6+543*21$
B15A	19222	$-12*(-34+5-(67+89A-B))$	$-BA-9+8+76+543*21$
B15B	19223	$12-3*(-4+567)*8-(-9A-B)$	$-B+A*98*7+6543-21$
B160	19224	$-1*23*4*(-56-(7+89))*(-A+B)$	$-B+A-(-9876+54*-32+1)$
B161	19225	$(-1+2^3*4*-5*(6+7))*8*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A-(9876-54*32)*-1$
B162	19226	$(-1-(2-3*(-4-5)*6*7))*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987+65-432+1)$
B163	19227	$12+34+(-567+8*-9A)*-B$	$B+A987-(65-432*1)$
B164	19228	$-1*2*(34-567-89-A)*B$	$B-(-A987-65-4-321)$
B165	19229	$-1-(2-3^4(4+5))+(-6*7+8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+65*(-4-3)*(-2+1)$
B166	19230	$((1-2^3)^4+5+6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9+8-7*(6-5*4)^3+2/1$
B167	19231	$1+2+(-3-456-789A)*-B$	$-B+A*9+8*7*6*(5+4+3+2-1)$
B168	19232	$-1+23+4*56-(7+8)*9A*-B$	$-B-A9-(-87+6-543*21)$
B169	19233	$-1-23+4567-89*-A*B$	$-B-A9+8+76+543*21$
B16A	19234	$1+23+4*56+(-7-8)*-9A*B$	$-B+A987+6+5*4*(3+21)$
B16B	19235	$1-23-(-4567-89A*B)$	$B-A9*(8-76-54-3)-(-2-1)$
B170	19236	$12*(34+5-6-78+9AB)$	$-BA+98-7-6-543*-21$
B171	19237	$1+2+3^4(4+5)-(-6+7*8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9+8*(7+6*5+4*3)^2-1$
B172	19238	$12-3+4*5*678-(-9A+B)$	$B+A+9+8/7^4(6-5-4-3+2)*1$
B173	19239	$1*(-23-4*56*7-(-8-9A))*-B$	$-BA-(-9-87+6)+543*21$
B174	19240	$12345-67*8*9+AB$	$-BA+9+8+76+543*21$
B175	19241	$(-1-(-2*-3-4^5-5*6^7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA+9876+5*(4+321)$
B176	19242	$-1-2*-34*56-7+89A*B$	$BA98+7*-6-(5+43*21)$
B177	19243	$-12-3-456*(78+9-AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2-1$
B178	19244	$1*-2-3-4*-5*678-(-9A-B)$	$-B-A9-(-87-6+543*21)$
B179	19245	$(-1+2^3*4*-5*(6+7))*8*9+A+B$	$B+A+9+8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2+1$
B17A	19246	$1-23-4+(56+78)*(-9+AB)$	$B-(-A-9876-54*32+1)$
B17B	19247	$(-1+(2+3)^4*5)*6-7*-8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9876-54*32*-1$
B180	19248	$-1*2*(-34-5678-9-(A-B))$	$-BA-(-98+7)-(-6-543*21)$
B181	19249	$-12-3*(-4567-8-9A*B)$	$B-A98-(-7+(6-543)*21)$
B182	19250	$-12-(-3-4567+89*-A*B)$	$B*(A98+76-543)*2*1$
B183	19251	$1+(-2*-3-4^5-5*6^7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-BA+9+8+7+6+543*21$
B184	19252	$1*-2*(-34-(5678-9)-(A-B))$	$BA98-7-6*5-43*21$
B185	19253	$1-2-(34-56)+78*(9A)*B$	$-B+A987-6*5+432+1$
B186	19254	$-1-2*3-(-4567+89A*B)$	$B-A9-(-87+6-543*21)$
B187	19255	$-1-2-(-3-4567)-89A*-B$	$-BA-98-7*-654*3+21$
B188	19256	$1*2*(34+5678-(9A)+B)$	$-B-A+9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2-1$
B189	19257	$-1-2+3*456*(-7+8)*9-A+B$	$-B-A+9*8-7*(6-5*4)^3-2*1$
B18A	19258	$((1-2^3)^4-5*(6-7))*8+9-(A-B)$	$-B-(A-9)-(-8+7+6-543*21)$
B18B	19259	$-1-2*3*-4*-567-(-89A+B)$	$BA-98+7*-6+543*21$
B190	19260	$-1*2*(-34-5)*6*7*8-(-9+AB)$	$-B-(-A-(-9+8)-(-7-6))-543*-21$
B191	19261	$-1+23-(45*6*7*8-9AB)$	$BA+9-(8+7)-(6-543)*21$
B192	19262	$((1+2*3)^4-5+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$B-(A-(-9+8))-7+6+543*-21$
B193	19263	$(-1-(-2*-3-4^5-5*6^7)*8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4+3)+2-1$
B194	19264	$-1+2+3*(4567+8+9A*-B)$	$B-(A-9)-(8-(-7-6-543*-21))$
B195	19265	$-1+2+3+4567+89*-A*-B$	$B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4+3)+2+1$
B196	19266	$-12-34+5*(-67-89)*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7-6*5-43*21$
B197	19267	$-123-45*-67+89AB$	$B+A987+6*-5*-4+321$
B198	19268	$1-2*-3+4567+89A*B$	$B+A-9+8*((-7*(6-5))^4+3*2)/1$
B199	19269	$(-1+(-2-3^4)*5+6)*(-7*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-9+8*((7/(6-5))^4+3*2)+1$
B19A	19270	$-1+2345+67+89AB$	$-B+A987-6-5-(-432+1)$
B19B	19271	$1*2345-(-67-89AB)$	$-B-(A-9+8*(-7+6))-543*-21$
B1A0	19272	$1+2345+67+89AB$	$-B*(-A98-7-65+4*(-3-21))$
B1A1	19273	$1+2*(3-4)*(56+7)*(8-9-AB)$	$BA-9-(-8-7-(6-543)*-21)$
B1A2	19274	$-1-2-3*(-4-5)*6*7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6*-5-432*1)$
B1A3	19275	$(1^2+3^4(4-5+6))*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6*-5+432+1$
B1A4	19276	$-1-2*3^4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9)-(-8-7)-6-543*-21$
B1A5	19277	$12+3*(4567+8+9A*-B)$	$B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4+3+2)-1$
B1A6	19278	$12*(345-6-(78+9A*-B))$	$B-A+9-8+7-6-543*-21$
B1A7	19279	$1+2*(-345-67+89)*(-A-B)$	$-B+A987-(-6*(54+32)+1)$
B1A8	19280	$((1-2^3)^4-5-(6+7))*8+9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987-(-6+5+432))-1$
B1A9	19281	$1+234*(56-7)-8*-9*(A-B)$	$BA98+7+6*-5*(4+32+1)$
B1AA	19282	$(-1+(2^3*4+5)*6*7*(8+9)+A+B)$	$-B-(-A987+6)-(-5-(432+1))$
B1AB	19283	$-1*(-234+5-67*8*(9+A+B))$	$-B+A987+6-(5-432)*1$
B1B0	19284	$1+234-5-67*-8*(9-(A-B))$	$-B-(-A+9+87)-(6-543*21)$
B1B1	19285	$-1*(-2-3-(4-(-56-78)*(-9+AB)))$	$BA98+7-6-5-43*21$
B1B2	19286	$1+2+3+4*5*(-678-9-A+B)$	$B+A+9+8*((7/(6-5))^4+3*2^1)$
B1B3	19287	$-1+23+4567-89*-A*B$	$B+A+9*8-7*((6-5*4)^3+2)*1$
B1B4	19288	$-1*2*(-34-5678-9-A+B)$	$BA-98-7-6+543*21$
B1B5	19289	$1+23-(-4567+89*-A*B)$	$B+A987-6*-5*-4*(-3-2)-1$
B1B6	19290	$1*(2-3-456)*(78+9-AB)$	$-B+A+9+8-(7-6)-543*-21$
B1B7	19291	$1-(2-3^4(4+5))-6*(7-8*9)+A-B$	$B-(A-9876)-54*(-32-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B1B8	19292	$1^2 * (34+56) * (7 - (-89+A) - B)$	$-B + A987 + 6 + 5 - (-432 + 1)$
B1B9	19293	$1 + 2 - 3 * (-4567 + 89A + B)$	$B + A987 - 6 - 5 - 432 * -1$
B1BA	19294	$-1 * (-2 + 345 - (6 - 7 - 89A)) * -B$	$B + A987 - (6 + 5 - (432 + 1))$
B1BB	19295	$-1 - 2^3 * 45^6 - 78^9 * (-A - B)$	$-B + A9 - 8 - 76 - 543 * -21$
B200	19296	$1^2 * (34 + 5678 - 9A + B)$	$B + A987 - 6 * (-54 - (32 - 1))$
B201	19297	$-1^2 * 3^4 * 4^5 * (-5 - 6 - 7^8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$BA987 - (-6 + 5 - 43 * -21)$
B202	19298	$123 + 4567 + 8^9 AB$	$B + A + 9 * 8 - 7^6 * (6 - 5^4) \wedge 3 - 2 - 1$
B203	19299	$-1^2 * 3^4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A + B$	$-B + A - 9 - 8 - 7^6 - 6 + 543 * 21$
B204	19300	$123 + 4^5 * (6 + 7 - 8^9 - A) - B$	$BA - 98 - 7 + 6 - 543 * -21$
B205	19301	$123 + 4^5 * 678 + 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A987 - 6 * (-54 - 32) - 1$
B206	19302	$1 + 2 - 3^4 * 56^7 - 7 - 89^8 - AB$	$B - (A - 98 + 76 + 543 * -21)$
B207	19303	$-1 - (2^{\wedge} 3 + 4) * -5 * (-6 - 7)^8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 - (6 - 5) * (-432 + 1)$
B208	19304	$(-1 - 2^3 * (3 - 4^{\wedge} 5) + (-6 - 7)^8) * 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 - 5 + 432 - 1$
B209	19305	$1 - (2^{\wedge} 3 + 4) * -5 * (-6 - 7)^8 * 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 - 5 - 432 * -1$
B20A	19306	$12^2 * (-3 - (-45 + 6) - (78 - 9AB))$	$B + A9 - (87 - (-6 + 543 * 21))$
B20B	19307	$-1 - 2^3 * 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 - A^* B$	$BA98 - (-7 - 6) - (-5 - 43 * -21)$
B210	19308	$1 + 2^* (-3 - 4 + 5678) + 9A + B$	$B + A987 + 6^* (54 + 32 + 1)$
B211	19309	$-1 - 2 - 3^* (-4567 + 89A) - B$	$B + A + 9 + 8^* ((7 / (6 - 5))^{\wedge} 4 + 3^{\wedge} 2) - 1$
B212	19310	$-1 - 2^{\wedge} (3 + 4) + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$B - (-A - 9 - (-8 + 7) - 6 + 543 * -21)$
B213	19311	$-1^2 \wedge (3 + 4) + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$-B + A9 + 8 - 76 + 543 * 21$
B214	19312	$-1 - 2^{\wedge} (3 + 4) + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$-BA^* (9 - 8^* (76 + 5) - (-432 - 1))$
B215	19313	$1 + 234 - (-567 - 89) * (A + B)$	$-B - A + 9 + 8 - 7^6 - 6 - 543 * -21$
B216	19314	$-1 - 2^* 3^4 * 567 - (-8 - 9A - B)$	$B + A - (-9 - 8 - (7 - 6)) - 543 * -21$
B217	19315	$(-1 + (-2 - 3 - 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^{\wedge} 7) * 8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A987 + 6 + 5 + 432 * 1$
B218	19316	$(-1^{\wedge} 2^* - 3^{\wedge} 4^* - 5 - 6) * (7^8 - 8 + 9) + A - B$	$B + A987 + 6 - (-5 - 432 - 1)$
B219	19317	$-1 + 2 - (345 - 6 + 7 + 89A) * -B$	$B + A9 - 8 - 76 + 543 * 21$
B21A	19318	$1 + 2^{\wedge} 3^* - 4^* (-5 - 6 - 7^8) * 9 + A + B$	$B + A9 - 87 + 6 - 543 * -21$
B21B	19319	$-1 - 2^{\wedge} 3 - 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 - A^* B$	$BA - 9 - 8 - 7^6 * (5 - 4) * -321$
B220	19320	$-12 - (-34 - 56 - 78^9 + 9A) * B$	$B + A987 - 6^* 5^* (4 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
B221	19321	$-1 - 2^3 * 4^5 * (5 - 6) * 7^8 * (-8 - (9A - B))$	$-B^* - A + 9 - 8 - 7^6 * (6 - 5^4) \wedge 3 + 2 / 1$
B222	19322	$(-1 + 2^3 * 4^{\wedge} 5 - 6^{\wedge} 7) * 8^9 + A - B$	$B + A - 98 - 76 - 543 * -21$
B223	19323	$-123^* (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - (-8 + 9A) + B)$	$B + A - 98 - 7 - (-6 - 543) * 21$
B224	19324	$-1 - 2^* (3 - 4 - 5678) + 9A + B$	$BA98 - 76 + (5 - 43) * 21$
B225	19325	$1 + 2^3 * 4^5 * 567 + 8 + 9A + B$	$-BA - 9 + 8^* 7^* (-6 + 54 - 32 + 1)$
B226	19326	$12 - (-3 + 4^5 - 5^6 * 78) - 9^* (-A - B)$	$BA - 9 + 8 - 76 - 543 * -21$
B227	19327	$1 - (2^{\wedge} 3 + 4) * -5 * (-6 - 7)^8 * 9 + A + B$	$BA98 - 765 + 4^* - 32^* 1$
B228	19328	$(-1 / -2 - 3^4) * -5^6 * 6^7 * 7^8 + 9 + A - B$	$BA + 9 - (8 + 76 - 543 * 21)$
B229	19329	$-1 - 2^3 + 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 - A^* B$	$BA + 9 - (87 - 6) - 543 * -21$
B22A	19330	$-1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 - A^* B$	$B + A + 9 + (-8^7 + 6^{\wedge} 5) / (4 - 3 / 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
B22B	19331	$1 + 2^* (-3 + 456) * 7 - 8^9 - 9A^* B$	$BA98 - 765 + 4^* (-32 + 1)$
B230	19332	$-1^2 * (-34 - (5678 + 9A + B))$	$-B + A98 - 7^6 * 65^* (4 - 32 + 1)$
B231	19333	$(-1 + 2 - 3) * (-4^{\wedge} 5 + 6 - 7^8) * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A9 + 8 - 76 + 543 * 21$
B232	19334	$1 + 2 - 345^6 * 7 - 89^8 A + B$	$B + A987 + 6^* 5 - 432^* -1$
B233	19335	$-12 + 345 + 6^* (-7 - 8 - 9) * -AB$	$B - A + 9^* 8 - (7 + 6 - 543 * 21)$
B234	19336	$-1 - 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - 6^7 * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9^* (8 + 7) + (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4)^* (3 / 2 + 1)$
B235	19337	$1 + 2 + 3^* (4567 - 89A) + B$	$B - A - 9 - 8 + 7^6 - 654^* - 3 - 21$
B236	19338	$-1 - 2^* (34 - 5678 - 9A) - B$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7^6 * 654^* 3 - 21$
B237	19339	$1 + 234^* 56 - (78 + 9A) * B$	$-BA - (-98 - 76 - 543 * 21)$
B238	19340	$123 - 45 - 6 - 78^* (-9 - A) * B$	$B + A987 + (-65 + 43) * -21$
B239	19341	$1 + 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - 6^7 * 8 - 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A + 9^* (8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
B23A	19342	$((1 - 2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A + 9^* (8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 \wedge 1$
B23B	19343	$-1^* (-2 / -3 + 4^5) * (-6 - 7)^8 * 9 + A - B$	$-B - A - 9 - (-8 - 76 - 543 * 21)$
B240	19344	$-123 - 4 - (56 + 78 - 9) * -AB$	$BA98 + 7^* (-6 + 54) * -3 - 2^* 1$
B241	19345	$(-1 + (-2 - 3) * 4^{\wedge} 5) * (6^* - 7 + 8) / 9 + A - B$	$B + A^* - 9 - 8 + 7 - (-6 - 543) * 21$
B242	19346	$-12 + 34^* (-5 - 6 + 7) * (8 - (9A + B))$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7^6 * 654^* 3 + 2 - 1$
B243	19347	$-1^* (-2^* (-3 - 4^5) * 6^* + 7) * 8^9 - A - B$	$-B + A - 9 - 8 + 76 - 543 * -21$
B244	19348	$-12^* (-3 + 45 - (6 - (-7 + 8) + 9AB))$	$-BA + 9 + 8 - 7^6 (654^* - 3 + 2) - 1$
B245	19349	$-123 - 4^5 * (6 - 789 + AB)$	$-B - A - 9 - (8 - (7 - 6) + 543) * -21$
B246	19350	$(-1 / -2 - 3^4) * -5^6 * 6^7 * 7^8 + 9 + A + B$	$B - A + 98 + 7^6 - 6 + 543 * 21$
B247	19351	$((-1 - 2) * -3^* (-4 - 5^6) * 6^7) * 9 - (A - B)$	$B + A + 9 + (8 + 7^* (-6 - 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 \wedge 1$
B248	19352	$-1^2 * 34^* (-5 - (6 - 78) - (9A + B))$	$B + A + 9 + (8 + 7^* (-6 - 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
B249	19353	$-1^2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - 6^7 * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B - (A + 98) - (-7^6 * 654^* 3 + 2^* - 1)$
B24A	19354	$-1 - 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - 6^7 * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$B + A - 9 - 8 - 76^5 * (-4 - 32 - 1)$
B24B	19355	$-1 - 2 - 3^{\wedge} 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$-BA - 9 + 8 + 7^6 * 6^* (54 - 3 - (2 + 1))$
B250	19356	$-1^2 - 2^* (-34 + 5678 - 9A + B)$	$-B - A + 9^* (8 - 7^6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge} (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1))$
B251	19357	$-1 - 2 - 3^{\wedge} 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$-B - A + 98 - (7 + 6) - 543^* - 21$
B252	19358	$1 + 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - 6^7 * 8 + 9 + A - B$	$-B + A987 + 65 + 432 - 1$
B253	19359	$-12 + 34^5 * (-6 - 7)^8 - 9AB$	$-B + A987 + 65 + 432 * 1$
B254	19360	$1^2 * -34^* (-56 - 7 + 89 - A) * -B$	$-B - A - (-9 - 87) - 6 + 543 * 21$
B255	19361	$1 + 2 - 3^{\wedge} 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A - B$	$BA - 9 + 87 - (-6 + 543) * -21$
B256	19362	$-12^* (-3 + 4^5 - 5 - (67 + 89A) - B)$	$-B - (-A + 9) + 87 - (6 + 543^* - 21)$
B257	19363	$1 + 2^{\wedge} 3^4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 - A^* B$	$-B + A^* 9 - (-8 - 7 + 6) + 543 * 21$
B258	19364	$1^2 * (3 - (-4 - (5678 + 9^* A)) - B)$	$B - (A - (-9 + 87) - (-6 - 543^* - 21))$
B259	19365	$-1^* (2 + 3)^{\wedge} 4^* (-5^6 + 7 - 8) - 9A - B$	$-B - (-A - 9 + 8 - 76) + 543 * 21$
B25A	19366	$-1 + (-2^* (-3 - 4^5) * 6^* + 7) * 8^9 + A - B$	$-B^* - A + 9 + 8^* ((7 / (6 - 5))^{\wedge} 4 + 3 + 2) - 1$
B25B	19367	$12 + 3 + 4^5 * 6 + (-7 - 8) * 9A - B$	$BA + 9876 - 54^* - 32 - 1$
B260	19368	$-1^* (-23 - 4^* (5 - 67)) * 8^9 * (A - B)$	$BA + 9876 - 54^* 32^* - 1$
B261	19369	$-1 + 2^* (-34 + 5678 - (9A - B))$	$B + A9876 - 54^* - 32 + 1$
B262	19370	$-1^2 * (34 - 5678 - 9A - B)$	$B + A + (-9 - 8 + 7) * (-6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 + 3^{\wedge} 2) - 1$
B263	19371	$((-1 - 2) * -3^* (-4 - 5^6) * 6^7 + 8) * 9 + A + B$	$B^* (-A9 + 8 + 76 + 54^* (3 + 21))$
B264	19372	NA	$-B - (A - 9) - (-87 - 6) - 543^* - 21$
B265	19373	$-1 - (2 - 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) - (6^* - 7 + 8) * 9) + A - B$	$BA98 + 7 + 65 - 43 * 21$
B266	19374	$12345 + 6^7 * (-8 - 9A) - B$	$BA98 + 76 - 5 + 43^* - 21$
B267	19375	$-1 + 2^* - 3^* - 4^* (567 + 8) + 9 + A - B$	$B + A + ((-9 + 8 - 7)^* - 6 + 5) * (-4 - 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
B268	19376	$1 + 2 + 34^5 * (6 + 7) * 8 - 9AB$	$B - A9 + 8 - (-7^* - 654^* - 3 + 2^* 1)$
B269	19377	$-1 + 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) + (6^* - 7 + 8) * 9 + A - B$	$BA98 - 765 + 43^* - 2^* 1$
B26A	19378	$1^2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) + (6^* - 7 + 8) * 9 + A - B$	$BA98 - 765 - 43^* 2 + 1$
B26B	19379	$1 + 2 + 3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) + (6^* - 7 + 8) * 9 + A - B$	$B - A - 98 - 7 - 6 + 543 * 21$
B270	19380	$-1 - 2^* - 3^* - 4^* - 567 + 8^9 + AB$	$B + A987 + 65 + 432 - 1$
B271	19381	$1^{\wedge} 2 - 3^{\wedge} 4 + 5^6 \wedge 7 / 8 / 9 + A + B$	$B - (-A987 - 65 - 432 * 1)$
B272	19382	$((1 - 2^* - 3) \wedge 4 - (-5^6 + 7)) * 8 - 9 + A - B$	$B + A987 + 65 + 432 + 1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B273	19383	$-1*(2+3)^4*(-5*6+7-8)+9+A-B$	$-B-A-9*-8*-7*(-6-5)*(4-3/2+1)$
B274	19384	$-12+3*-45*(6-7+8-9A-B)$	$-B-(-A+98)-(7-6)-543*-21$
B275	19385	$12345+6*7*(-89-A-B)$	$B+A-9+8+76+543*21$
B276	19386	$1*-23*(4*56-789+AB)$	$B-A*(-9+8)+76-543*-21$
B277	19387	$-1+2*(-3-45*(-67-89))+A*-B$	$BA+9*-8-(-7*6+543*-21)$
B278	19388	$-1*(2-3+45+67+8+9)*-AB$	$-B-(-A987-6*5*4*-3*-2*-1)$
B279	19389	$-1*(-2*(-3-4*5)*-6+7)*8*9+A+B$	$B+A-9*8*(7-6*(-5*4+3)^2)^1$
B27A	19390	$-12*(3-4*-56-7*(89+AB))$	$B+A+9*(-8-7*(6-5^4+3))/2+1$
B27B	19391	$-1-2*(-3+4-(5678-9-A*-B))$	$BA-98+76-543*-21$
B280	19392	$-1*2*(34-5678-9-AB)$	$-B+A+9+87+6-543*-21$
B281	19393	$1-2+345*-6*-7+8*(9-AB)$	$BA9-8*(-76+5)*(43-21)$
B282	19394	$(-1+2+3-4^4-5*6^7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B-(A-9)-(-87-6+543*-21)$
B283	19395	$-1-(2-3^4+5)-(6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	$-BA+9+87-(6+543)*-21$
B284	19396	$(-1-2*3^4)*(-5+6)*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A-98+7*654*3+2+1$
B285	19397	$1-(2-3^4+5)-(6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	$B+A-9*8+7-(-6^5*(4+3/-2)-1)$
B286	19398	$123+4*-5*-6-78-(-9A+B)$	$B-(-A-9*87)-6*5*(-432-1)$
B287	19399	$-1+2+3^4(4+5)+(6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	$B-(-A-98+7+6)-543*-21$
B288	19400	$-1*2*345*(67+8-9A+B)$	$BA98-(765+4)+3*-21$
B289	19401	$1^2+3^4(4+5)-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA-9-8+7-6+543*21$
B28A	19402	$(-1+2)*3^4(4+5)-6*(7*8-9)-(A-B)$	$BA98-7+6*54*3-2-1$
B28B	19403	$1+2+3^4(4+5)-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-765-43-21$
B290	19404	$-12*-3*(-456-78*(9-A-B))$	$-B*(-A9-876+54-321)$
B291	19405	$(-1-(-2-3)^4)*(5/(6-7)*8+9)+A-B$	$BA-(-9+8)-(-7-(-6-543*-21))$
B292	19406	$1*-2*(3+4)*(-5678-9A+B)$	$B+A9-(8+7)+6+543*21$
B293	19407	$-1*2^3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6*54*-3+2*1$
B294	19408	$1*-2*(3-4-5678-9A+B)$	$-B+A987-(6-543+21)$
B295	19409	$1*2-3*4+5*6^7/8/9-(A+B)$	$B+A987-6*-5*4*-3*-2-1$
B296	19410	$-1-23-45*-67+89AB$	$B+A987+6*-5*(4-(3+21))$
B297	19411	$1*-23-45*-67+89AB$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)*(-6^5/4+3+2*1)$
B298	19412	$-1*(-23+4)*(-5+678-(9A-B))$	$BA98+7*-65-432+1$
B299	19413	$123-4*5*-678-9+AB$	$BA-9-(8-7-6+543*-21)$
B29A	19414	$-1-2*3^4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B+A9+8-(-7-6-543*21)$
B29B	19415	$-1*2*3^4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B*(A-987-(-65-4+321))$
B2A0	19416	$1-2*3^4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-87*6)*(-5-43+21)$
B2A1	19417	$(-1/-2+3)*(4+(-5-6)*7*-8*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*54*3-2*1$
B2A2	19418	$-12*(3-4)*(-5*(6-7)*-8+9AB)$	$BA+9-8*(7-6)-543*-21$
B2A3	19419	$12-(3-4)-56-(7-8)*-9A*-B$	$BA+9-(8-7-(-6-543*-21))$
B2A4	19420	$-1+2*(34-(-5678-9))+AB$	$-B-(-A987-6-543)-21$
B2A5	19421	$-12-(3-45*67-89AB)$	$-B+A987-6-(-5*4*32+1)$
B2A6	19422	$1*2*(3-4-(-5678+9-AB))$	$-B-(-A987-(-6-5*-4*32*1))$
B2A7	19423	$-12+345*-6*-7-8*9A+B$	$-B+A987-6-5*4*-32+1$
B2A8	19424	$-1-2-3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$B-(-A9-8)-(-7+6)-543*-21$
B2A9	19425	$-1-2-3-4*-5*(678+9)+AB$	$BA98-765-(43+2)-1$
B2AA	19426	$1-2*3+4*5*(678+9)+AB$	$-B*(A98+76-5*4*3*-2)*-1$
B2AB	19427	$-12+3+45*67+89AB$	$BA98-765-(43+2-1)$
B2B0	19428	$1-2-3+4+5-6-(7+8)*9A*-B$	$BA98-765+43*(-2+1)$
B2B1	19429	$1*2-3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-(765+43)-(-2+1)$
B2B2	19430	$1+2-3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-765-43+2*1$
B2B3	19431	$1-2-3-4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-(765-(-43+2+1))$
B2B4	19432	$-1-2-3+45*67+89AB$	$-B+A987-6+543-(2-1)$
B2B5	19433	$-1-23*-456-(-7-8)*(9+AB)$	$-B+A987-65*-4+321$
B2B6	19434	$-1-2-3-45*-67+89AB$	$-B+A987-6-(-543-2)-1$
B2B7	19435	$1+2-3-4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B-(-A987+6)-(-543+2*-1)$
B2B8	19436	$-1-(-2+3)-(-45*67-89AB)$	$BA98-765-(4+32+1)$
B2B9	19437	$-1*(-2-(-3-45*-67)-89AB)$	$BA98-765-4+32*-1$
B2BA	19438	$1*2*(-3+4+5678-9+AB)$	$-BA-98*-76+5*4*321$
B2BB	19439	$-1-2-3+4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$-B-A*-9+8*(-76+5*-4)*(3-21)$
B300	19440	$-1*23*(-456-7-8*9-A+B)$	$B+A+(-9+8-(7-6^5))*(4-3/2)-1$
B301	19441	$1+23*4*(-5+67-(-89+A)+B)$	$B+A+(-9+8-7+6^5)*(4-3*2^1)$
B302	19442	$-1-(-2+34)-(-5-6-(7+8)*9A*B)$	$BA98-765-4*3-21$
B303	19443	$123-4+(-56-78)*(9-AB)$	$-B+A987+6+543+2*-1$
B304	19444	$1+2+3-45*-67+89AB$	$BA98-765+4-32-1$
B305	19445	$-1+2*(3-4)*(-5+6-78+9A*-B)$	$B-(-A987+6+5*-4*32)+1$
B306	19446	$-12*(34+5-(6-7)-(-8+9AB))$	$-B+A987+6+543+2-1$
B307	19447	$1^2+3+4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA-9*-8-7*6+543*21$
B308	19448	$1*2*(3-(4-5678-9A)+B)$	$-B+A987-(-6-543-2)+1$
B309	19449	$12-3+45*67+89AB$	$-B-A98*(-7-6)-(-543-2)+1$
B30A	19450	$-12+3*(-4-567-8)*(-9-A+B)$	$B-A+9+8*-76*(-5+32-1)$
B30B	19451	$1+23*56+7+89*(-A-B)$	$-B+A*9+87-6+543*21$
B310	19452	$-1*2*(3-4-5678-9A-B)$	$B+A987-(-6-543)-2-1$
B311	19453	$-1+2-3*(45-6-7*(8*9A-B))$	$BA98-765-4-(-3+21)$
B312	19454	$1*-2*(-3*-45*(-67+8+9)+AB)$	$-B+A987+6+5*4*(32+1)$
B313	19455	$12+3+45*67+89AB$	$B+A987+65*4+321$
B314	19456	$1+2+3*4+5*6^7/8/9-(A-B)$	$B+A987+6+5*4*-32*-1$
B315	19457	$-1-234*(-56+7)+89-A+B$	$B+A987-6+543+2*1$
B316	19458	$1*-2*(3+4-5678-9-AB)$	$B+A987-6+543+2+1$
B317	19459	$12+345+67*8*(9+A+B)$	$-B-A+9+8-7*-654*3-21$
B318	19460	$12*(-3+45-67-8+9AB)$	$-B-A+98+76+543*21$
B319	19461	$-1-(2+3+4)+5-6-(-7-8)*9A*B$	$BA98-765+4-(-3+21)$
B31A	19462	$-1+23-4+5*-6-(7+8)*9A*-B$	$B-(-A9+87+(-6-543)*21)$
B31B	19463	$1*2*3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8-7)^6*5/4/3+2*1$
B320	19464	$-1+23+45*67+89AB$	$B+A987-(-6-(543-2-1))$
B321	19465	$1-2+(-3-4^4-5/-6^7)*8*9+A-B$	$B+A9+8*7*6+543*21$
B322	19466	$1+23-(-45*67-89AB)$	$B+A987+6-(-543+2-1)$
B323	19467	$(-1*-2-3/4)*(5^6+7)-8*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6+543*(2-1)$
B324	19468	$-1*2*(-34-(-5+67)*(-8+9)*AB)$	$B+A987-(-6-543-2+1)$
B325	19469	$1+2+(-3-4^4-5/-6^7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-765-(4+3+2+1)$
B326	19470	$1*(-2-3)*(45+6)*(-7+8*9-AB)$	$-B+A987+6+543+21$
B327	19471	$-12+3*(4-(5-6))*(-7-(-8-9A*B))$	$BA98-765-4-3-2+1$
B328	19472	$1+2^3*4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-7*6*(54-32)*1$
B329	19473	$1*2^3*4+5*6^7/8/9-(A-B)$	$BA98-765-(4+3-2+1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B32A	19474	$12^*(34-5-67-(-8-9AB))$	$BA98-765-4-3+2^*1$
B32B	19475	$1-2+3-(-4-5+6-(-7-8))^*-9A^*B$	$BA98-765-4-3-(-2-1)$
B330	19476	$1+2^*-3^*4^*(-567-8)-(-9A+B)$	$BA98-765+(4-3)^*-2-1$
B331	19477	$-1+(-2-3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*-7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-765+4-3^*2^*1$
B332	19478	$(-1^*-2+3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-765-4-3^*(-2+1)$
B333	19479	$1+(-2-3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*-7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-765-(4-3-2+1)$
B334	19480	$(-1/-2+3/4)^*(5^*6+7^*8-9)-A^*B$	$BA98-765-4+3+2^*1$
B335	19481	$-1^*2+3^*(4+5)+(-6-7)^*(8+9)+A+B$	$BA98-(765+4-3^*-2^*-1)$
B336	19482	$1+23^*-4^*-56-(789+A)^*-B$	$BA98-765-4+3^*2+1$
B337	19483	$-1-(-2-(-3-4^*-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-(765+4+3)-(-2-1)$
B338	19484	$(-1+2^*3)^*(4+5-6^*7/(-8^*9))+A-B$	$BA98-765-4-3^*(-2-1)$
B339	19485	$1-(-2-(-3-4^*-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-765+4+3-2+1$
B33A	19486	$-1^*2^*(-3-4-5678-9-AB)$	$BA98-765+4+3^*(2-1)$
B33B	19487	$(-1-((2+3)^4+5+6))^*-7^*8/9+A-B$	$BA98-765-(-4-3-2)-1$
B340	19488	$-12^*(-34-5-67+8)^*(-9+A+B)$	$BA98-765+4+3+2^*1$
B341	19489	$-1+234-56-78^*(-9-A)^*B$	$BA98-765+4+3+2+1$
B342	19490	$-1+2-(3+4^*-56-78^*(-9-A)^*-B)$	$BA98-(765+4+3^*-2)+1$
B343	19491	$123+4^*-5^*(-678-(9-A+B))$	$B-A+9-(8+7^*654^*-3-2+1)$
B344	19492	$-1^*(-23-456-789+A)^*B$	$B+A987-(-6-543)+21$
B345	19493	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4^*5+6+7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-65^*(-4^*-3-2^*-1)$
B346	19494	$-123^*(-4-5-67+89-AB)$	$BA98-765-(-4^*3-2-1)$
B347	19495	$-1-((-2-3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$BA+9-8^*(7+6-(-54^*-32-1))$
B348	19496	$-1-2^*(-34-(5678+9A))-B$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6+5)^*(4^*(3+2)+1)$
B349	19497	$-1+23+4-(-5-(6+78))^*-9^*(-A-B)$	$BA98-765-4-3+21$
B34A	19498	$((1+2)^3+4)^*(-5+6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A-9+87+(6+543)^*21$
B34B	19499	$(-1-2-3-4)^*-5^*-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7^*-6^*-5-43^*21$
B350	19500	$(-1^*-2+3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*7^*8-9+A+B$	$BA98+76^*-5+432^*-1$
B351	19501	$1-2^*(-34+5)^*67+89A^*B$	$-B+A+(-987+6)^*(-5-4-(3-2^*-1))$
B352	19502	$-12^*(3+4)^*(-56-7-89-A-B)$	$-B-(-A9-87)-6+543^*-21$
B353	19503	$1+2+3^*(4+5)+6-7-8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98-(765+4^*3^*2^*1)$
B354	19504	$1^*-2^*(-34-56)^*(7-8-9A+B)$	$-BA+98+765^*(-4-3+21)$
B355	19505	$-1-(-2-(-3-4^*-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A+B$	$BA98-765-(-43+21)$
B356	19506	$-1234+567^*(8+9+A)-B$	$BA-9+8-(-76-543^*21)$
B357	19507	$1-(-2-(-3-4^*-5^*-6^*7)^*8)^*9+A+B$	$B+A-9-(-8^*7-6^*5^*(4-3/2)+1)$
B358	19508	$-12+3+(-45-67-(8+9))^*-AB$	$BA+9-8-76-543^*-21$
B359	19509	$1^*(23+4+5-678-9)^*(-A-B)$	$B+A-98^*-7^*(-65-(-43-2))^*-1$
B35A	19510	$1^*2^*(34-(-5678-9)-A^*-B)$	$B+A+9-8^*(-7^*-6^*(-5^*4^*3+2)+1)$
B35B	19511	$((-1-2)^3+4+5+6)^*7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-765+4-(-3-21)$
B360	19512	$((1-2^*3)^4+5+6+7)^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-765-4+32-1$
B361	19513	$-1^*-2^*((3+4-(-5-6)^*7)/8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-765-4-32^*-1$
B362	19514	$-1-23^*(4+56)-(-7-8)^*9AB$	$BA98-(765+4-32)+1$
B363	19515	$-1+2-3+45-6+(-7-8)^*9A^*-B$	$BA98-765-4^*-3^*(2+1)$
B364	19516	$12^*(-3-4+56-78+9AB)$	$BA98-765-4^*-3+21$
B365	19517	$-1-2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A-B$	$BA-98-(7^*654^*-3-2)+1$
B366	19518	$-1^*2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A-B$	$-B+A-9+87+(-6-543)^*-21$
B367	19519	$-1+2^*34^*(-5^*-6+78-9+AB)$	$B+A+9-8^*-7^*-6^*(-5^*4^*3+2)+1$
B368	19520	$1234+56-78^*-9^*(A+B)$	$BA98-(765-4)-(-32+1)$
B369	19521	$1^*2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-765+4-32^*-1$
B36A	19522	$-1^*-2^*(-3-4-(-5+67)^*(8-9-AB))$	$BA98-765-(-4-32-1)$
B36B	19523	$1+2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A-B$	$BA+9+87+6+543^*21$
B370	19524	$1^*2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9-(A-B)$	$BA+9+8+76-543^*-21$
B371	19525	$-1^*(-2/-3-4^*-5^*6^*7)^*8^*9-A^*B$	$-BA+98-7^*(-654-3)^*(2+1)$
B372	19526	$-1+2+34^*-56^*-7-(-89+A)^*B$	$B+A+9^*8-7+6^*5^*(4-3/2)^*1$
B373	19527	$-1^*(2+(-3-4)^*5^*(-6-7^*8)^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-765-(-43-(-2-1))$
B374	19528	$-1+(2+3/-4)^*(5^*6+(7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-(765-43+2^*1)$
B375	19529	$-1+2^*(34+5678-(-9A-B))$	$BA98-(765-43+2-1)$
B376	19530	$-1^*2^*(-34-5678-9A-B)$	$BA98-765+43^*(2-1)$
B377	19531	$12-3-4^*5^*(6-789+AB)$	$B+A987+6^*54+321$
B378	19532	$1-((2+3)^4-5)/(6/7-8/9)-(A-B)$	$B-A+9-(8-765^*(-4-3+21))$
B379	19533	$((-1-2)^3+4+5+6)^*7+8+9+A+B$	$BA98-(765-43-2)+1$
B37A	19534	$(1^*2-(3+4)^5)/-6^*7-8^*9+A-B$	$BA+98+7-6-543^*-21$
B37B	19535	$-1-(2-3^*(4+5))-6^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA+9+87+6+543^*21$
B380	19536	$-1^*-2^*(-3+4+5+678-9A)^*B$	$B^*(-A9-8-(-76+5-4^*321))$
B381	19537	$-1+(-2-3)/-4^*(5^*6+7)+8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*5^*(4+32^*-1)$
B382	19538	$12+3^*4^*5-6-(-7-8)^*-9A^*-B$	$BA98-7+6^*5^*(-4+32)+1$
B383	19539	$1^*2+3^*(4+5)-6^*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+9-(8-7-6)^*5+4^*(3^*2+1)$
B384	19540	$-1^*(-2+3/4)^*(5^*6+7+8)-9+A-B$	$BA98+7^*(-65-4)-321$
B385	19541	$1-((-2+3/4)^*(5^*6+7+8)+9)+A-B$	$B-A^*-9^*-87+6^*54^*-3^*-21$
B386	19542	$1-2^*(3+(-4^*5-(6+7^*8))^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A9-(8-7+(-6-543)^*21)$
B387	19543	$(-1^*2^*3)^4+5+(-6-7)^*8^*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-654+3^*21)$
B388	19544	$12^*(3-(-45+67+8)+9AB)$	$B+A+(-9-8^*(7+6^*5))^*-4^*3-(-2-1)$
B389	19545	$1+2+3^*4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A+B$	$-B-A-9^*((-8-7)^*(6-5+(-4^*3)^2)+1)$
B38A	19546	$-1+23+4^*5^*(6-7)^*8^*(9-AB)$	$-B-A^*-98+7+6^*5^*(432-1)$
B38B	19547	$(1+2)^3+4+5^*6^*7/8/9+A-B$	$B^*(-A-(-987+6^*54-3-(-2-1)))$
B390	19548	$-1-2+3-4^*(-5^*678-9A+B)$	$B+A-9-8^*(7^*-6+5)^*(4^*3+2^*1)$
B391	19549	$-1^*(2+(-3-4)^*5^*(-6-7^*8)^*9)+A+B$	$-BA+9^*(8+765+4-3)^*2-1$
B392	19550	$12+3^*4^*(-5+67)^*(-8+9+A+B)$	$BA98-765-4+3^*21$
B393	19551	$-1^*2+3^*(4+5)+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6^*5^*(-4+32)^*-1$
B394	19552	$-1^*-2^*(34+5678-(-9-AB))$	$-BA+98^*76+5432^*1$
B395	19553	$-1-2^*(3+4)-(-5/(6-7-8))^*9+A-B$	$-BA-98^*-76+5432+1$
B396	19554	$1^*2+3^*(4+5)+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654+3^*-21$
B397	19555	$1^*2+3^*(4+5)+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-765-(-43-21)$
B398	19556	$1+2+3^*(4+5)+6+(-7-8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8^*((-7-6^*5)^*(4^*3+2)-1)$
B399	19557	$-1+(-2-3)/-4^*(5^*6+7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654-32-1$
B39A	19558	$1-2+34-(-56-78+9)^*AB$	$BA98-765+4+3^*21$
B39B	19559	$(1+2^*3)^4+((5+6)/7+8)+9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-654+32-1)$
B3A0	19560	$-12+3456-7+89^*AB$	$B+A-9^*(8+7-6^*(5+4)^3/2+1)$
B3A1	19561	$1+2^*-3^*4^*5^*(-67-89+A+B)$	$B+A+(-9-8+7)^*(-6^*5/4-3^*2-1)$
B3A2	19562	$-1^*-2^*(3^*-45-(-67+8)^*(9+AB))$	$-B-A+(-9/-8+7+6+5)^*4^*(3+2)-1$
B3A3	19563	$(1+2)^3-3^*(4+5)^6-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9^*8^*(7^*6^*5+4^*3-2)^*1$
B3A4	19564	$(-1+(-2+3^*4)^*-5^*6)^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7^*65-(-4+321)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B3A5	19565	$-1-2+3^{(4+5)}-6*7-8^9+A-B$	$-B-A-9-8^7+(6^5+4)^3/2-1$
B3A6	19566	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5*6^{\wedge}7/8/9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*(7^*-6+5)*(4^3+2^{\wedge}1)$
B3A7	19567	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8^9+A-B$	$BA98-765-4*(3-21)$
B3A8	19568	$1+23+4+56-(-7-8)*-9A^*-B$	$BA98-(-7+654)+3*-21$
B3A9	19569	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8^9+A-B$	$-B*(-A98+7*6*-5-4*-3-21)$
B3AA	19570	$-1*2*(-3+4)*(-5678+9*(-A-B))$	$B+A-9*(8+7-6*(5+4)^3/2)+1$
B3AB	19571	$-1-2+3456-7+89*AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)*((-7-(6+5))^4+3+2)*1$
B3B0	19572	$-1*(2+34)*5(-678+9AB)$	$BA98-7*65+4-321$
B3B1	19573	$1-2-(-3456-(-7-89*-AB))$	$B-(-A9-8+7*(654-3)*(-2-1))$
B3B2	19574	$-12+3456+7-89*-AB$	$-B+A987+654+3-21$
B3B3	19575	$-1+2+3456-7+89*AB$	$B+A-9*(8+7)+6-((-5-4)*3)^(2+1)$
B3B4	19576	$((1+2*3)^{\wedge}4+5+6*7)*8-9-(A-B)$	$-B-A-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
B3B5	19577	$1+2-(-3456+7+89*-AB)$	$B+A+9*(8-7*(6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)))/2-1$
B3B6	19578	$12345+6*78*-9-AB$	$-BA-98^{\wedge}(-76-5*-4*(-3-2+1))$
B3B7	19579	$-1+(-2-3)/-4*(5^{\wedge}6+7+8)+9+A+B$	$B+A987+654-32-1$
B3B8	19580	$-1-2-(3+(-4-(5-6))^{\wedge}7+8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-765+43*2-1$
B3B9	19581	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$BA98-765-43*2*-1$
B3BA	19582	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$BA98-765+43*2+1$
B3BB	19583	$(1-2^{\wedge}3+4)^{\wedge}-5*-6^{\wedge}7*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9-8^7+(6^5+4)^3/2-1$
B400	19584	$-1+2^{\wedge}(-3*-4)+5^{\wedge}6+(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9-8^7+(6^5+4)^3/2/1$
B401	19585	$-1-(2-3456-(7-89*-AB))$	$-B-A+9-8^7+(6^5+4)^3/2+1$
B402	19586	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+(-6-7)*8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+(-8*-7+6)*5)*(4^3+2-1)$
B403	19587	$1-2+3456+7-89*-AB$	$B+A-9*((-8-7)*(6-5+(-4*3)^2)+1)$
B404	19588	$12+3456-7-89*-AB$	$B+A+(-9-8)*((-7-(6+5))^4+3+2-1)$
B405	19589	$-123-4*5*(-6-789+AB)$	$-B-(-A987-654-3*-2)-1$
B406	19590	$12+34+56+(-7-8)*-9A^*B$	$BA98-7-654-32-1$
B407	19591	$1+2+3456+7-89*-AB$	$BA98-7-(654+32*1)$
B408	19592	$((1+2*3)^{\wedge}4+5+6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(654+32-1)$
B409	19593	$-1+(-2+3^{\wedge}(-4*-5-6-7)-8)*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A987+654-3*(2-1)$
B40A	19594	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654-3+2-1$
B40B	19595	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654-3+2*1$
B410	19596	$1*-2*(3+4-5678+(9+A)*-B)$	$B+A987+654+3-21$
B411	19597	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654+3+2*-1$
B412	19598	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987-(-654-3+2)+1$
B413	19599	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654-3*(-2+1)$
B414	19600	$-12*-34*(56-(78+9))*A-B$	$-B+A987+654+3+2-1$
B415	19601	$1-2*(-3-(45-6))*(-7-8*-9+AB)$	$BA98-(7+654)-(-3+21)$
B416	19602	$12+3456-(-7+89*-AB)$	$B*(A+9+876+54+321)$
B417	19603	$1-2^{\wedge}3-((-4-(5-6))^{\wedge}7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8)*(-7-(6+5))^4+3-2^{\wedge}1$
B418	19604	$1*(2+3*-4*5)*(6+7)*(89-AB)$	$BA98+7-654-32-1$
B419	19605	$1+234-(-56-78)*(-9+AB)$	$BA98+7-654+32*-1$
B41A	19606	$-1*(2-3*(4-567*-8+9+AB))$	$BA98+7-654-32+1$
B41B	19607	$-1+23*4-5*-6-(-7-8)*9A^*B$	$BA98-7-654+3-21$
B420	19608	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7-8^9+A-B$	$BA98-7-65*4*3-21$
B421	19609	$123-45*-67+89AB$	$-B+A*(98+7-(-6-5)+4*321)$
B422	19610	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7*8-9+A-B$	$BA9+87*(6-54)*-3-21$
B423	19611	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7-8^9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+3*-2-1$
B424	19612	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7-8^9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-654+3+2+1)$
B425	19613	$1-2-3*(4-(-5-6*-789-AB))$	$B-(-A987-654+3)-2*1$
B426	19614	$1*2*(3+4)*(56-(78-9AB))$	$B-(-A987-654+3+2-1)$
B427	19615	$1-2*-345-67*(-89-AB)$	$BA98+7-654-3-21$
B428	19616	$-1*(-2*3*((4+5+6)^{\wedge}7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-(654-3+2))-1$
B429	19617	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987-(-654+3)+2*1$
B42A	19618	$1-(2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))+(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+3-2-1$
B42B	19619	$(-1-2*3-4^{\wedge}-5/-6^{\wedge}-7*8)*9+A-B$	$B-A98*8*(-76-5+43+21)$
B430	19620	$-1*(23-(-456+7)-8)*(-9-A-B)$	$B+A987+654-(-3+2-1)$
B431	19621	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+654)+3-21$
B432	19622	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+3+2-1$
B433	19623	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7-8^9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-3-2-1$
B434	19624	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+3*-2*-1$
B435	19625	$-1+2*3*(-4*(-567+8)+9A-B)$	$BA98-(7+654+3+2-1)$
B436	19626	$-12-34*(567+8-9A*B)$	$BA98-7-654+3*(-2+1)$
B437	19627	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(654+3-2+1)$
B438	19628	$-12*(3-4-56-(-78+9AB))$	$-B+A+98+7*-654*-3+21$
B439	19629	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6/(7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-3+2+1$
B43A	19630	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-65*4*3*(2+1)$
B43B	19631	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(765+4*32*-1)$
B440	19632	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-765-43*(-2-1)$
B441	19633	$-1+(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*-8^9+A-B$	$-B+A987+654+32-1$
B442	19634	$1234+567*(-8+9-(-A-B))$	$-B+A987+654-32*-1$
B443	19635	$1*(2-(-34-567)-8*-9A)*B$	$BA9+87*-6*(5-4*-3*2)*-1$
B444	19636	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-(3*-2-1)$
B445	19637	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654-3*2*1$
B446	19638	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654+3*(2+1)$
B447	19639	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+654)-3-(2-1)$
B448	19640	$-1*(-23+45-6)*(-789+AB)$	$B+A987-(-654-(-3+21))$
B449	19641	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654-3+2-1$
B44A	19642	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-(-654-3+2)*-1$
B44B	19643	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*7-8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+654)-3+2+1$
B450	19644	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-65*-4*-3-2-1$
B451	19645	$1+23*456+(-78-9A)*-B$	$BA98+7-(654-(3-2))+1$
B452	19646	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)*4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A-B$	$B-(-A987-654)-(-3-21)$
B453	19647	$-1*(234+5)*(-67+8-(9-A)+B)$	$BA98+7-654-(-3-2)-1$
B454	19648	$(-1/-2-3)*(-4^{\wedge}5+6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8-7*(6^5+4)^3/2-1$
B455	19649	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654-(-3-2-1)$
B456	19650	$1*(-234+56-(-7-89))*-AB$	$BA98-(-7-(-654-3*-2+1))$
B457	19651	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-3+21$
B458	19652	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6*7-8^9+A-B$	$-B-A-9+(8-7+6+5*4)^3-2+1$
B459	19653	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6*7-8^9+A-B$	$BA98+76*-5-(4+321)$
B45A	19654	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-(8*7-(6^5+4)^3)/2*1$
B45B	19655	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+32-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B460	19656	$-1*2*-3*-4*(-567-8+9-(A+B))$	$B+A987+654-32*-1$
B461	19657	$1*2+(-3-4^A-5*6^A7^8)*9+A-B$	$B+A987+654+32+1$
B462	19658	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)-6*7+8+9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8+7*(6+5-4^A3)^A2-1$
B463	19659	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6*7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8-(7+6)+(5+4)^A(3+2^A-1))$
B464	19660	$-1*2*(-3+4-(5+6))*(7-8*(9-AB))$	$B+A-9-8+7*((6-(-5+4^A3))^A2-1)$
B465	19661	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98+76*-5+4-321$
B466	19662	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7+(6*5+4)^A3/2-1$
B467	19663	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7+(6*5+4)^A3/2*1$
B468	19664	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8+7+(6*5+4)^A3/2+1$
B469	19665	$-123*(-45+67+8*(-9-A)+B)$	$BA98+7-654-3+21$
B46A	19666	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-(-32+1)$
B46B	19667	$1-2+3^A(4+5)-6-7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654-32*-1$
B470	19668	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-654+32+1$
B471	19669	$1-2+3^A(4+5)-6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-(8-(7-(6*5+4)^A3)))/-2*1$
B472	19670	$12*(34+5+67+89A+B)$	$B+A+(9-8-7+(6*5+4)^A3)*2^A-1$
B473	19671	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6-7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654+3+21$
B474	19672	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6-7-8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-(-65*-4*3-21)$
B475	19673	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6-7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8+7+6+5^A)^A3/2*1$
B476	19674	$1+2^A(3*4)+5+6-7*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A-98*-76+5432+1$
B477	19675	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8)^A7+(6*5+4)^A3/2+1$
B478	19676	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7-8-9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8+7+(6*5+4)^A3)/2-1$
B479	19677	$1*(23-4+5-678-9)*(-A-B)$	$-BA+987-6*5*-432*1$
B47A	19678	$1-2-3+4^A-5*6^A7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-76-(543+21)$
B47B	19679	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6-7+8-9+A-B$	$BA(-9-87+(-6-543)*21)$
B480	19680	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-(654-32)-1$
B481	19681	$1-2-(3-4+5-6+7-8)^A9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654+32*1$
B482	19682	$1*(-2-34+567)*(-89+AB)$	$BA98-(-7+654)-(-32-1)$
B483	19683	$-1-2*-3*(-45-6)*7*8-(9+AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+(6*5+4)^A3/2*1$
B484	19684	$-12*(3-45+67-8-9AB)$	$B+A+9+8-7+(6*5+4)^A3/2+1$
B485	19685	$1+2-(3+4-5-6-7+8)^A9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7*(6+5-4^A3)^A2/1$
B486	19686	$12345-6*(78-9)*A-B$	$B+A+9-8+7*(6+5-4^A3)^A2+1$
B487	19687	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6+7-8+9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8-(7+6*5-4^A3)^A(2+1)$
B488	19688	$-1-2-(3*-4*(56-(7-89)))*-A-B$	$B+A-9-8-(7-6*5-4)^A3+2-1$
B489	19689	$1-2+34*5-6*7+(-8+9A)*B$	$BA98+7*(-6+5*4*-3*2+1)$
B48A	19690	$1*-2*(3-(4+567-(-89A)))*B$	$-B*(-A-9*8*7-6*54*-3*-2)*-1$
B48B	19691	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+65*(-4*3+21)$
B490	19692	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-B+A-98*-76+5432-1$
B491	19693	$1+2+(-3+4)*(-5+67+89)*A*B$	$B+A987+654-3*-21$
B492	19694	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7-8+9+A-B$	$B-A-98*-76+5432-1$
B493	19695	$-1+23*45*6+(78+9)*A*-B$	$BA+9*8+7*(-654*-3-(2-1))$
B494	19696	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$B-A+98*76+5432+1$
B495	19697	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6-7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8+7+(6*5+4)^A3/2*1$
B496	19698	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7-8+9+A-B$	$-BA9-(8*7-6*5*-43*-2+1)$
B497	19699	$-123-(-456-78*(-9-A)*-B)$	$-BA9-8*7*-6*5*-43*-2*-1$
B498	19700	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-543-2-1$
B499	19701	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+6-7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-(543+2*1)$
B49A	19702	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-543-2+1$
B49B	19703	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+(9+8+7-6+5+4)^A3-2+1$
B4A0	19704	$-1+23*-45*6+789*A-B$	$BA98-76-543+2-1$
B4A1	19705	$-12+3456+(-7+89A)*B$	$BA98-76-543-2*-1$
B4A2	19706	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76-543+2+1$
B4A3	19707	$1^A2*3^A(4+5)+6*7-8-9+A-B$	$-BA+987-6*-5*(432+1)$
B4A4	19708	$12345+6*78*-9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8-(7-6*5-4)^A3+2+1$
B4A5	19709	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6*7-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5*43*(2+1)$
B4A6	19710	$-1*23*(-4-56*(7-8-9-(A-B)))$	$B+A987-6*5*(4-32*1)$
B4A7	19711	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8+9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8-7+6+5^A4)^A3-2*1$
B4A8	19712	$-12*(-3-4-56-(-78+9AB))$	$-B*(-A-987-65*4+3*-21)$
B4A9	19713	$1+2^A(3*4)+5+6-7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98-(76+5*-4*-32+1)$
B4AA	19714	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5*4*-32*-1$
B4AB	19715	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8+9+A-B$	$-BA9+8-7*6*-5*-43*2*-1$
B4B0	19716	$-1*(23+4)*(567-8-9AB)$	$B+A-98*-76+5432+1$
B4B1	19717	$123+45*6-78*(9+A)*-B$	$-BA+9876-5*(-432+1)$
B4B2	19718	$-1+2^A(3*4)+5+6+(7-8)^A9+A-B$	$BA98+7-654-3*-21$
B4B3	19719	$1-23+456*7+89AB$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6*5-4)^A3-2*1$
B4B4	19720	$-1+2+3456+(-7+89A)*B$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6*5-4)^A3-2+1$
B4B5	19721	$12-(-345+6)-78*(-9-A)*B$	$-BA-(-9876-5*432)-1$
B4B6	19722	$1-(-2-3456+(7-89A)*B)$	$-BA+9876+5*432*1$
B4B7	19723	$1^A2*3^A(4+5)+6*7+8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*-432+1$
B4B8	19724	$12-3*(4+5)*(-6+7-8*-9*-A-B)$	$B+A+9+8-(7-6*5-4)^A3+2+1$
B4B9	19725	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8-9+A-B$	$BA-9*(87+6)*-5*4-32+1$
B4BA	19726	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6+7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7*-6-(543+21)$
B4BB	19727	$1+2^A(3*4)+5+6+7+8-9+A-B$	$-BA+9876-5*(-432-1)$
B500	19728	$-12-3-456*-7+89AB$	$BA98-76-543+21$
B501	19729	$1+2^A(3*4)+5+6+7-8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6*(-5-4)-321$
B502	19730	$-1+2*34-5+(-6-7)*8*9*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7+6*-54-321$
B503	19731	$1+2^A(3*4)+5+6-7+8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7*(65+4-32*-1)$
B504	19732	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8*(-7*-6*5+4^A3)+2)+1$
B505	19733	$12-(-345-6+78*(9+A)*-B)$	$B+A+(9+(8+(7-6)^A5)^A4)*3+2*1$
B506	19734	$-12-(-3+456*-7)+89AB$	$-B*(-A98+7*(-65+4+32+1))$
B507	19735	$1^A2*3^A(4+5)+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*8-(7-6*5-4)^A3+2-1$
B508	19736	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+6+7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9*8-(7-6*5-4)^A3+2^A1$
B509	19737	$1*(2-3-4+56+78)*(9A+B)$	$BA98+7-6*(54-3*-21)$
B50A	19738	$1-2-34*56*-7+89A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7+(6*5+4)^A3/2/1$
B50B	19739	$-1-2-(-3+456*-7-89AB)$	$BA98+7*6*-5-432-1$
B510	19740	$-12*-3*(-456+789A-B)$	$B+A+9-(-8+7^A6+5^A4)/(-3*2)-1$
B511	19741	$1-(2+3)+456*7+89AB$	$B+A+9-(-8+7^A6+5^A4)/-3*2^A-1$
B512	19742	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8+9+A-B$	$-BA-9+87*6-543*-21$
B513	19743	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6-7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(-6-5)*-4^A3/2+1$
B514	19744	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6+7*8+9+A-B$	$BA-9-(8*-7*6+543*-21)$
B515	19745	$-1-(2-3)-(-456*7-89AB)$	$B+A-9-(-8*7-(-6-((-5-4)^A3)^A(2+1)))$
B516	19746	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)-(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$-B+A987-65*(4+3)*-2*1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B517	19747	$1-2+3-(-456*7-89AB)$	$B+A-9*-8*(-7*-6*5+4^3)-2*1$
B518	19748	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-76*(5+4)-3*2*1$
B519	19749	$-1+2+3-456*-7+89AB$	$BA98-7*6-543-2*1$
B51A	19750	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7*6-543-2+1$
B51B	19751	$1+2+3+456*7+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6*5+4)^3/2-1$
B520	19752	$1+2*3-456*-7+89AB$	$B+A+9*8+7+(6*5+4)^3/2*1$
B521	19753	$1^A2*3^A(4+5)+6-7+8*9+A-B$	$-BA9+8*-7*6*-54+32*-1$
B522	19754	$1-2-345+(67+89)*-A*-B$	$-B-A+9*(-8+7-6+5*4)^3+2*1$
B523	19755	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-7+8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6-543-21$
B524	19756	$1*-2*(-34-5-(-6+7-8*9A))*-B$	$-BA98+76*(-5-4+321)$
B525	19757	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6+7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8+7*(6+5+4^3)^2+1$
B526	19758	$-1-234*5-6-(-7-8)*9AB$	$B+A-9^A(8-7)*-6*(5+4)^3/2+1$
B527	19759	$-12+3*(4567-8*(9+AB))$	$BA98+76*(-5-4)+3+2*1$
B528	19760	$1+2+3+((4+5-6)^A+7+8)*9+A-B$	$-BA+9-87*-6+543*21$
B529	19761	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+(-6+7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9-8*7)*-6*-5*(-4-3)*2^A1$
B52A	19762	$12+3-456*-7+89AB$	$BA98-7*6*5*4-32*-1$
B52B	19763	$1*2-34*56*-7+89A+B$	$BA98-7*6*5*4+32+1$
B530	19764	$1*23*(4+56+7+8-9-A+B)$	$-B*-A+(9-8)^A+7+(6*5+4)^3/2+1$
B531	19765	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A-9*(-8-7)+(-6*5-4)^3/-2-1$
B532	19766	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8*9+A-B$	$BA+987*(-6+5*4)-32*-1$
B533	19767	$1*2^A(3*4)+5^A6+7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-543-21$
B534	19768	$-12*(-3-45+67-8-9AB)$	$-B*-A-9+8+7+(6*5+4)^3/2*1$
B535	19769	$1-(2-34*56*7+8+9A*-B)$	$BA98+7-6-543-21$
B536	19770	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+6+7+8*9+A-B$	$-BA-9-8+7*(-65+4)*(-32-1)$
B537	19771	$-1+23-(-456*7-89AB)$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*(6-5+4)^3*2/1$
B538	19772	$(1^A2+3*4)^A-5*(6+7)^A8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*-8+7)*(6-5-4)^3*2+1$
B539	19773	$1-(-23-456*7)+89AB$	$B+A+9*8-(7-6*5-4)^3-2-1$
B53A	19774	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7*8+9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8-(7-6*5-4)^3-2^A1$
B53B	19775	$-12+3456-7+89A*B$	$B-(A9+87*-6-543*21)$
B540	19776	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7*-6-543+21$
B541	19777	$(-1+2)*3^A(4+5)-(-6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-(7+6)-(543+2+1)$
B542	19778	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6-543+2*-1$
B543	19779	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6-543-2+1$
B544	19780	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*-7*((-6-5)/(-4^A-3*2)+1)$
B545	19781	$(1+2)^A3+((4+5-6)^A+7+8)*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6-543-21$
B546	19782	$-12*3*(456-789)*(-A+B)$	$BA98-7-(6+543-2*1)$
B547	19783	$1-2*(3+4)*(5-6+7+8-9AB)$	$BA98-7-6-543+2+1$
B548	19784	$-1234-5*-6*-7*(-89-A+B)$	$-BA-9*(-8+76)*(-54+32-1)$
B549	19785	$1-2-(-34*-56*-7-8+9A*-B)$	$BA98-(-7+6)-5*4*(32+1)$
B54A	19786	$-1-2-(-3456+7+89A*-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8*7+6)*-5*(4^3+2+1)$
B54B	19787	$-1*(2-3456+7-89A*B)$	$-BA-98+(7+6)*-543*-2-1$
B550	19788	$1-2+3456-7-89A*-B$	$-B+A+987-6*5*(-432+1)$
B551	19789	$-12+3456+7+89A*B$	$BA98-7+6-(543-(-2-1))$
B552	19790	$-1*2*(-34-5-6-78*(9A-B))$	$B-A+987+6*5*(432-1)$
B553	19791	$-1*(-2-3456+7-89A*B)$	$-BA9-8*(7+65)*(-4-3-21)$
B554	19792	$1+2+3456-7+89A*B$	$BA98-7+65*-4-321$
B555	19793	$-1-2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(-6+543-(2-1))$
B556	19794	$1+23*(45-67*-8)+9A*B$	$BA98-7+6-543-2*-1$
B557	19795	$1-2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-(6+543-2+1)$
B558	19796	$12*(3+4)*(-5*6-(-78-(9+AB)))$	$BA98+7-6-543+2*1$
B559	19797	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+987+6*5*432-1$
B55A	19798	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-(-8*-7+6)*5)*(-4^3+2)-1$
B55B	19799	$1-2-3*(-45-6*789+AB)$	$B+A+(-9-(-8*-7+6)*5)*(-4^3+2)/1$
B560	19800	$1*-2*3*-4*(567-(89-AB))$	$B*A*(-98-76+54-32)*-1$
B561	19801	$-1*(2-3456-7-89A*B)$	$BA98-7*(6+54+32+1)$
B562	19802	$1-2+3456-(-7-89A*B)$	$-B-A-9-8*(-7-6*5)^*(4^3+2+1)$
B563	19803	$12+3456-(-7-89A*B)$	$BA98+7+6-(543+2)-1$
B564	19804	$-1+2+3456+7-89A*-B$	$BA98-7+6-5*4*32+1$
B565	19805	$1*2+(3+(4-(-5+6)))^A+7+8)*9+A+B$	$BA98-7-(6+543)+21$
B566	19806	$1+2+3456+7+89A*B$	$BA98+7+6+543*(-2+1)$
B567	19807	$1*2^A(3*4)+5^A6-7+8*9+A+B$	$BA98+7+6-(543-2+1)$
B568	19808	$1*2*(345-6-7+8*9*AB)$	$BA98+7+6-543+2*1$
B569	19809	$-1+2^A(3+4)-(-5/(6-7)-8)^A+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-(-6+543-2-1)$
B56A	19810	$1-(2-3^A(4+5)+6)-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6-543-21$
B56B	19811	$1+2^A(3+4)+(5/(6-7)+8)^A+9+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8+(7-6)^A+5+4)^3+2)-1$
B570	19812	$1^A2-(-3^A(4+5)+6+(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^3)+2+1)$
B571	19813	$1*2+3^A(4+5)-6+(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8+(7-6)^A+5+4)^3+2)+1$
B572	19814	$(-1+2-3*-4*-5)*-6*7*8-9+A-B$	$BA+9*8-(-7-6-543)*21$
B573	19815	$1+2-3*(45+6-7)*(-8-9-A*B)$	$-B-A-9*(8-7*(-6-5*-4^3+2)*1)$
B574	19816	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A+B$	$-B-A+9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^3)-2^A-1)$
B575	19817	$12+3456+7+89A*B$	$BA98-7-(-6+543-21)$
B576	19818	$-1*-23*(456-7-8-(-9A+B))$	$-B+A+987+6*5*432*1$
B577	19819	$1+2-34*5*6*-7-8*-9AB$	$BA98+7-6-543+21$
B578	19820	$1*2+3^A(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A+B$	$-BA9+8-7*(-6-5*432+1)$
B579	19821	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$B-A+987+6*-5*-432+1$
B57A	19822	$-1*-2*(-3-45+6+7+8*9A)*B$	$-B+A9*(-8+76)+5432+1$
B57B	19823	$(-1+2)*3^A(4+5)+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-5*-4*(-32+1)$
B580	19824	$12*(3-(-45-67-89A-B))$	$-B+A987+6-(5-43)*21$
B581	19825	$-1+(2^A3+(4+5-6)^A+7+8)*9+A-B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7/6)*(-5*-4^3+2)+1$
B582	19826	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(-6*(5-4^3)-2^A-1)$
B583	19827	$-12+3*-4*-5-(-67+8*-9)*AB$	$-B-A+(-9-8-7)*(6*(-5-4^3)*2+1)$
B584	19828	$-1*2+(3+4)^A+5+6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7*-65-43*21$
B585	19829	$-1-23*(-456-78)-(9-A-B)$	$-BA9-8*7*-6*54+32*1$
B586	19830	$1^A2*(3+4)^A+5+6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA+98-7*6*(-5-4-321)$
B587	19831	$1^A2+(3+4)^A+5+6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6-543+21$
B588	19832	$1*2+(3+4)^A+5+6*7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^3)+2^A-1)$
B589	19833	$1+2+(3+4)^A+5+6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7*-6-543+2*-1$
B58A	19834	$1^A2-(-3^A(4+5)+6+(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	$B+A-9-(-8*-7*-6*(-5+4^3)+2)*1$
B58B	19835	$(1+2^A3)*((4+5-6)^A+7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA-98*76+5432-1$
B590	19836	$123*-4*(-56-(78-(9A+B)))$	$BA-98*-76+5432*1$
B591	19837	$1+2-3*(-4^A5*6+7*-8*9)-A*B$	$BA98+7+6+5*-4*(32-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B592	19838	$1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)+5^{\wedge}6+7+8-9+A*B$	$B+A+9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2*1)$
B593	19839	$(-1+2*3)^*-4^{\wedge}5*(6-7/8-9)+A-B$	$B+A+9*(8+7+6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
B594	19840	$12345+6*78*-9+AB$	$B+A-9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
B595	19841	$-1/-2*-3*-4^{\wedge}5*(6+7)-(8+9)-A*B$	$B+A+987+6*5*432+1$
B596	19842	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8-9-(A+B)$	$-B-A-(-9876+5*-432)-1$
B597	19843	$-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/(6/7-8/9)+A-B$	$B-A9*(8-76)+5432*1$
B598	19844	$-1*-2/3^{\wedge}-4+(5/(6-7)+8)^{\wedge}9+A-B$	$-B-(A-9876-5*432)+1$
B599	19845	$1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/(6/7-8/9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*-5*4*-3+21$
B59A	19846	$(-1-((-2-3^{\wedge}4)*5*6+7))*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6-5*4*-32*-1$
B59B	19847	$12345+6*7*(-8-9A+B)$	$B+A+9*(8+(7+6/(5-4))^{\wedge}3-2)-1$
B5A0	19848	$1+23-4-(5+67)*(-89-AB)$	$B+A+9*(8+(7+6^{\wedge}(5-4))^{\wedge}3-2/1)$
B5A1	19849	$-1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7*8*9+A+B$	$B+A+((-9-8)*(-7*-6-5^{\wedge}4)+3)*2*1$
B5A2	19850	$-1*2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7*8*9+A+B$	$B+A-9+(8*7-6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}1$
B5A3	19851	$1-2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7*8*9+A+B$	$BA98-7*6*(5+4*3)+2-1$
B5A4	19852	$-1+(-2+3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*-7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2*1$
B5A5	19853	$1^{\wedge}2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5+6*7*8*9+A+B$	$-B-A+9*-8*(-7+6*5)*-4*3+2/1$
B5A6	19854	$1+(-2+3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5-432-1$
B5A7	19855	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5-432*1$
B5A8	19856	$-1*2*(-345*-6-(-7+89)*AB)$	$BA98-76-5-432+1$
B5A9	19857	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)*((4+5-6)^{\wedge}7+8+9)+A+B$	$B+A-9*(8-7*(-6-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2)*1)$
B5AA	19858	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3*-4)+5^{\wedge}6-(-7-8)*9-(A-B)$	$BA98+76-543-21$
B5AB	19859	$-1/-2*-3*(-4^{\wedge}5*(6+7)+8*9)+A-B$	$-BA+9*8-7*(-65+4)*(32+1)$
B5B0	19860	$((1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5*6)*(7+8)-9-(A+B)$	$B-A+9876+5*(432-1)$
B5B1	19861	$(-1+2*3)*-4^{\wedge}5*(6-7/8-9)+A-B$	$BA-98*(7+6)*5*(-4+32)-1$
B5B2	19862	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8-9+A-B$	$-B-(-A-9876-5*432)-1$
B5B3	19863	$-1234-5*6*7*-89-AB$	$-B-A-9-87*-6-543*-21$
B5B4	19864	$(-1-((-2-3^{\wedge}4)*5*6+7))*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76+5-(432+1)$
B5B5	19865	$1+234+56+(-7-8)*9A*-B$	$BA98-7-(65+432+1)$
B5B6	19866	$12*3*(45-6+7+8-9-A)*B$	$-B+A987-65-43*-21$
B5B7	19867	$1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/(6/7-8/9)+A+B$	$BA98-7-(65-(-432+1))$
B5B8	19868	$-1-(2-3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8*7-6)*-5*4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}1$
B5B9	19869	$1+2-34*56*-7+(8+9A)*B$	$B+A+(-9-8*7)*(6*(-5-4^{\wedge}3))^2+1$
B5BA	19870	$-12-3-(4-5)*(-678+9)*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7*(6+5)*(-4-3-2)-1$
B5BB	19871	$-1*(2^{\wedge}3+4)*(5*-6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8*7-6)*-5/4^{\wedge}-3+2-1$
B600	19872	$1-2+3456+(7+89A)*B$	$BA98+7*(-6-5)-432+1$
B601	19873	$1+2*3*-4*(-5+6)*-78*-9*(A-B)$	$BA98-7*(6+5)-432*1$
B602	19874	$-1+2+3456+(-7-89A)*B$	$B+A-9*(-8+7*(-6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)-1$
B603	19875	$1*2-3*-4*(5*-6+7)*-8*9-(A-B)$	$B-A98-7*-6*5*-43*2*-1$
B604	19876	$-1+2-3*(45+6*-789)*(-A+B)$	$B+A-9*(-8+7*(-6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)+1$
B605	19877	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-(-7-8)*9+A+B$	$BA98+7*-65-4*(32-1)$
B606	19878	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3*-4)+5^{\wedge}6-(-7-8)*9+A+B$	$BA98+7*(-6-54-3-21)$
B607	19879	$-1+(-2-(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+65)-432+1$
B608	19880	$12-34*-56*7-(-8-9A)*B$	$BA98+76-543-2-1$
B609	19881	$1+(-2-(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-(-65-432+1))$
B60A	19882	$((1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5*6)*(7+8)-9-(A-B)$	$BA98-(-76+543)-(2-1)$
B60B	19883	$(-1+(-2*3)^{\wedge}4-5*-6)*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$BA98+76+543*(-2+1)$
B610	19884	$-1-234*5*-6+7*(8+9AB)$	$BA98+76-543+2-1$
B611	19885	$-12-34*-56*7-8+9AB$	$BA98+76-543+2*1$
B612	19886	$(-1-((-2-3^{\wedge}4)*5*6+7))*8+9+A+B$	$BA98-(-76+543-2-1)$
B613	19887	$-1+(-2-((-3+4-5^{\wedge}6)/7+8))*9-A*B$	$-BA9-8*76*(-5-4+32+1)$
B614	19888	$-1*2*(34+56+7)*-8*(-9+A)*B$	$B+A987-(65+43*-21)$
B615	19889	$12345-6*-7*(8+9-AB)$	$-B-A+(-9-(-8*7-6^{\wedge}5/4))*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
B616	19890	$1-(-2-3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8*(-7+6*5)*-4*3-2-1$
B617	19891	$-1*(-2-3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9-(A-B)$	$B+A+9*8*(-7+6*5)*-4*3-2/1$
B618	19892	$-1-(2^{\wedge}3+4)*(5*-6+7)*8*9+A+B$	$BA98+7*(6-54-32)*1$
B619	19893	$-1*(2^{\wedge}3+4)*(5*-6+7)*8*9+A+B$	$B+A98+7*-65*(4-32)*1$
B61A	19894	$1-(2^{\wedge}3+4)*(5*-6+7)*8*9+A+B$	$BA98+76+5*4*-32*1$
B61B	19895	$-1+2-3*-4-(5-(678-9)*A+B)$	$B-A*(-9-876)-(-5-4321)$
B620	19896	$-12+3-4*-5+(-678+9)*(-A-B)$	$B+A987-6*(54+3)*(-2-1)$
B621	19897	$1*(-2-34-56+7)*(-8-9*(A+B))$	$-B*-A-9-8*-7*(-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
B622	19898	$-1+23*(-45+6-(-7-(-8-9))-A)*-B$	$BA98-76+54*3*(-2-1)$
B623	19899	$1^{\wedge}2+(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*-8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6*(5+43)*2*1$
B624	19900	$-1+2-(-34*56*-7+8-9AB)$	$B+A+(-9*(8+7)-6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-2*1$
B625	19901	$1+2+(-3-4^{\wedge}-5/6^{\wedge}7)*-8*9+A-B$	$-B+A+9+87*6-543*-21$
B626	19902	$1+2-34*56*7-(8-9AB)$	$BA98-7*6-5-432-1$
B627	19903	$1+(-2-(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+(9+8+7+6*5*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
B628	19904	$-1-234*-56-(78-9)*(A+B)$	$BA98-7*6-5-432+1$
B629	19905	$(-1+(-2*3)^{\wedge}4-5*-6)*(7+8)+9+A+B$	$B+A-9+87*6+543*21$
B62A	19906	$1^{\wedge}2-(-3^{\wedge}(4+5))+(-6-7)*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$-B-A-9-8*-7*(-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2^{\wedge}1)$
B62B	19907	$(-1-2*3)*(-4*-5-6*7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+(-65+43)*21$
B630	19908	$12*(-3-(4-(-5+6-7)-(8+9AB)))$	$BA98+76-543+21$
B631	19909	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6*7+8*9+A*B$	$-BA-9876-5*-4321$
B632	19910	$-1-(-2-3*-4*(5*-6+7)*8)*9+A+B$	$B*-A*(-98+7+6*5-4+32*-1)$
B633	19911	$(-1+(-2-3^{\wedge}4)*-5*6*(7-8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9+8*7)*(-6*-5+4)*-3*(2+1)$
B634	19912	$-1-(2+34*56*-7-8-9AB)$	$BA98-7-6*5-432-1$
B635	19913	$(-1-2/3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*-8*9+A*B$	$-B-A-(-9*8*7+(-6^{\wedge}5+4))*(3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
B636	19914	$1-2*(3-4*-5*(6-7*8*9))+A-B$	$BA98-7*6+5-432+1$
B637	19915	$-1-(-2+(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9*(8-(7-6))+5)*(-4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
B638	19916	$123+456*7+89AB$	$B+A*-9*-8-76-543*-21$
B639	19917	$1-(-2+(-3-4^{\wedge}-5*6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9+A-B$	$-B*-A-9-8*(-7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2-1)$
B63A	19918	$-1*-2*(-34+56+7*(-8+9AB))$	$B+A+9+8+(-7*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
B63B	19919	$(-1+2+3+4)*-5*(6-7*8*9)+A-B$	$-BA9-87*(6+54)*-3+2*1$
B640	19920	$((1+2+3)^{\wedge}4+5*6)*(7+8)+9+A+B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
B641	19921	$1*(-2+3*-456+7-8+9A)*-B$	$BA98+7-(65-43)*21$
B642	19922	$-1+23+4+5+(678-9)*(A+B)$	$B+A987+65*-4*(-3-(2-1))$
B643	19923	$-12-3+45+(678-9)*(A+B)$	$-B-A+9*8*7+6^{\wedge}5*(4-3/2)^{\wedge}1$
B644	19924	$-1+(-2*-3)^{\wedge}4*(-5/-6+7/8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7*65-43*2+1$
B645	19925	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}-5*-6^{\wedge}7*8)*9+A-B$	$B+A+(9*8*7+(6*5+4)^{\wedge}3)/2^{\wedge}1$
B646	19926	$1*-2*(-34-(-5+6))*(7+8+9AB)$	$BA98+7-6*5-(432+1)$
B647	19927	NA	$BA98+7-6*5+432*-1$
B648	19928	$-1-2-34*(-5+6*-7-8)*9+AB$	$BA98-(-7-6*-5-(-432+1))$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B649	19929	$(-1-2^*3)^*(-4^*-5-6^*7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$B+A+(-9^*-8+7)^*(6+5^*(4+3)^2+1)$
B64A	19930	$-1+2^*3^*-4^*(5+6+7+8-9)^*-A+B$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8^*+7+6)+5)^*-4^*3^2+1$
B64B	19931	$123-4^*-5^*(6+789-AB)$	$BA98-7-6-5-432-1$
B650	19932	$-1+(-2-(3-4^*-5/-6^*-7))^*-8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98-(765+4-321)$
B651	19933	$-1/-2^*(3^*-4^*5^*(6+7)-8^*9)-(A-B)$	$BA98-7-(6+5)-432+1$
B652	19934	$(-1-2)^*(3-4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7^*6^*(5+4-3^*-2^*1)$
B653	19935	$-1-2^*(3+(-4^*5-6^*(7+8))^*9)-A^*B$	$B+A987-6^*5-43^*-21$
B654	19936	$1-2^*(3-4^*-5^*(6-7^*8^*9))+A+B$	$B-A9+8+(7+6)^*543^*-2^*-1$
B655	19937	$-1-(-2+(-3-4^*-5^*6^*7^*8)^*9)+A+B$	$-B^*-A+9^*(8+(7+6^*(5-4))^3-2/1)$
B656	19938	$(1-(2+3))^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A-B$	$-B^*-A+((-9-8)^*(-7^*-6-5^*4)+3)^2*1$
B657	19939	$1-(-2+(-3-4^*-5^*6^*7^*8)^*9)+A+B$	$BA98-7+6^*(5-4-3-2-1)$
B658	19940	$1^*-2-3^*-4^*(5^*-6^*7^*8-9)-A^*B$	$BA98-765+4+321$
B659	19941	$-1-234+5+(-678-9)^*(A-B)$	$BA98-7-(6-5+432+1)$
B65A	19942	$-1+2^*3^*(45+6)^*7^*8+9+A^*B$	$-B+A987-(6-(5-43^*-21))$
B65B	19943	$(-1+2)^*-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-5-432-1$
B660	19944	$1^2-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+6-5-43^*-21$
B661	19945	$1^2-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-5-(432-1)$
B662	19946	$-1-2+3^*(-456-78)^*-9+A+B$	$BA98+7-6-5-432^*1$
B663	19947	$-12-(-345-6-(7-8)^*9A^*B)$	$BA98+7-6-5-432+1$
B664	19948	$1+2-3^*(-4^*5^*6+7^*-8^*9)-(A-B)$	$B+A-9-8^*-7^*(-6^*(5-4^3)+2^*1)$
B665	19949	$(-1^*2^*3)^4+5^*-6-7^*8^*9-A-B$	$BA98+7^*-65-(43+21)$
B666	19950	$-1/-2^*-3^*-4^*5^*(6+7)-(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A-9^*8^*7-6+5^*4^3(3^*2)+1$
B667	19951	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4-5^*(6-7^*8^*9))+A-B$	$-B-A+9+(-8^*+7+6)^*(-5^*-4^3+2)-1$
B668	19952	$((1+2)^4(3+4)-5^*6/(7-8))^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+(8^*7+6)^*(-5^*-4^3+2)^1$
B669	19953	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4-5+6+7^*8+9+A-B)$	$BA98-(7-6-5)-(432+1)$
B66A	19954	$-1+(2+3)^4+5^*6^*7^*8/9-A^*B$	$-B+A987+6+5-43^*-21$
B66B	19955	$(1-2^*3)^4+5^*6^*7^*8/9-A^*B$	$BA98-7+6+5-(432-1)$
B670	19956	$1^2*2^*(-345+67+8^*9A^*B)$	$BA98+7-6-(-5-432^*-1)$
B671	19957	$(-1-((-2-3^*4)^*5^*6+7))^*8-9+A^*B$	$BA98+7+6-5-432-1$
B672	19958	$1+2-3^*(4+5+6-7)^*-8-9-A^*B$	$-B-A98-(-76-543)^*21$
B673	19959	$(-1/-2+3+4)^*(-5^*-6+7)^*8^*9-A-B$	$-BA9-8^*7^*(6+5+4-3-2-1)$
B674	19960	$(-1^*2^*3)^4+4^*(5-(-6+7)/8)-9-(A-B)$	$BA+987+6^*5^*432-1$
B675	19961	$12345-6^*(7+8-9)^*AB$	$BA+987+6^*5^*-432^*-1$
B676	19962	$1^*(-2-3-4)^*(-567+8-9AB)$	$-B-A-9^*8^*7+6+5^*4^3(3^*2)+1$
B677	19963	$1-(2-3^*4(4+5)-6^*(7^*8-9))+A-B$	$B+A+(-9^*8+7+6)^*(5-(4+3)^2(2+1))$
B678	19964	$-1/-2^*-3^*(-4^*5^*(6+7)+8)+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5^*43^*2^*1$
B679	19965	$(-1+2)^*-3^*(-4^*5^*6-7^*8^*9)+A+B$	$-B-(A+9)-(-8^*-76-543^*21)$
B67A	19966	$((-1^*-2+3^*4)^*5^*-6+7)^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A987+6-5+43^*21$
B67B	19967	$1/2^*3^*4^5/(6+7)^4(8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6+5-432-1$
B680	19968	$-1^*-2^*(3^*-4-56)^*(-7+8-9A-B)$	$BA98+7+6-(-5+432^*1)$
B681	19969	$(-1^*2^*3)^4+5^*-6-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6-(-5+432)+1$
B682	19970	$12+3^*-4^*(5-6-7^*(8+9AB))$	$B+A+(-9^*-8/7+6)^*(-5^*(4+3))^2-1$
B683	19971	$1-2-3^*-4^*567-8^*9A^*B$	$B+A+(9^*-8/-7+6)^*(-5^*(4+3))^2/1$
B684	19972	$-1/-2^*-3^*-4^*5^*(6+7)-(8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A98+7+6^*5^*432^*1$
B685	19973	$-1^*-2^*3^*(4-5^*(6-7^*8^*9))+A+B$	$BA98-7^*65-43-2+1$
B686	19974	$(-1+(-2^*3-4^*5)^*-6^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-(7-6^*5)-(432-1)$
B687	19975	$(-1-((-2-3^*4)^*5^*6+7))^*8+9+A^*B$	$B+A+9^*(8+(7+6-5^*4^3)^2)+1$
B688	19976	$(-1^*2^*3)^4+4^*(5-(-6+7)/8)+9+A-B$	$B^*(-A-98+765-43)^2*1$
B689	19977	$1-2^*3+4-(5-6+7+8)^*-9AB$	$B+A-9-(-8-7)/(6+5)^4(-4+3-2)^*1$
B68A	19978	$12^*(3-45+6^*7-(-8-9AB))$	$BA-98^*(-76-(5+43)-21)$
B68B	19979	$-1+23^*4^*(5-6-7^*-8-(-9-AB))$	$-B-A98-7^*(65-4)^*-32^*-1$
B690	19980	$-1^*23^*(456-7+89)^*(A-B)$	$B+A98-7^*6^*5^*-432^*1$
B691	19981	$-1/-2^*3^*(4^*5+6-7^*8^*9)+A-B$	$B+A-(9+(8^*(7+6)-5)^*4^3(-3^*-2)-1)$
B692	19982	$(-1/-2+3^*-4^*5)^*-6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-(-9^*(8+(-7^*(-6-5^*4)+3)/2)+1)$
B693	19983	$((1+2)^4(3+4)+5^*6+7+8)^*9+A+B$	$-B-A+9+8^*7+6+5^*4^3+21$
B694	19984	$-1/-2^*-3^*-4^*5^*(6+7)+8+9+A-B$	$-BA-9-8^*7^*-6^*-5^*-4^*3-21$
B695	19985	$1+((-2-3^*4)^*5^*-6+7)^*8+9+A-B$	$-B+A-9-8^*-76-543^*-21$
B696	19986	$12+3^*-4^*-567-8^*-9A^*B$	$BA98-7^*-6-(5+432+1)$
B697	19987	$1-(2-3^*4(4+5)+6^*(7+8)^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6^*5+432^*-1$
B698	19988	$-1-2-3^*-4^*-5^*-6-7+89AB$	$BA98+7^*6-5-432+1$
B699	19989	$-1^*(2-3^*-4^*-5^*6-7-89AB)$	$B+A+(9^*8+7-6+5)^*4^3(3+2-1)$
B69A	19990	$1-(2-3^*-4^*5^*-6-7-89AB)$	$B+A-9^*8^*7-6+5^*4^3(3^*2)-1$
B69B	19991	$-1-2-(-3^*(4567-89^*A)-B)$	$BA+987+6^*-5^*(-432-1)$
B6A0	19992	$-1^*(-2-34)^*(5-678+9AB)$	$B+A-9^*8^*7-6+5^*4^3(3^*2)+1$
B6A1	19993	$1+(2^*3+4)^4/5/(6+7-8)-9-(A-B)$	$BA98+7^*(-65-4+3)-21$
B6A2	19994	$-1234+5^*6^*7^*-89^*(-A+B)$	$BA98+7-6^*5^*-4-321$
B6A3	19995	$-1234-5^*6^*7^*-89-(A-B)$	$B-A^*9^*-87+6+5^*4^321$
B6A4	19996	$-1+(-2-((-3+4-5^*6)/7+8))^*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+(8+7)^*(6+5)^4(4-(3-2))+1$
B6A5	19997	$1+234^*56-7^*(89+AB)$	$BA98-76+5^*-4-321$
B6A6	19998	$-1^*2^*(-3^*-4^*-56-7-(-8+9A))^*B$	$B^*(A9-8^*(-76-54)+321)$
B6A7	19999	$(1+2+3+4)^4/5/(6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$-B+A^*(987-6-5-(-432+1))$
B6A8	20000	$1+(2^*3+4)^4/5/(6+(7-8)^9)+A-B$	$BA9-87+6^*-5^*(-432+1)$
B6A9	20001	$((1+2)^4(3+4)+5)^*((-6+7)/8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-7^*6-54-321$
B6AA	20002	$(-1^*-2+3^*4)^*(-5^*(6-7^*8-9)+A-B)$	$BA98+7^*-65-4^*-3^*-2+1$
B6AB	20003	$-1/-2^*(-3^*-4^*5^*(6+7)+8^*9)+A-B$	$-B+A-(-9-8^*76-543^*21)$
B6B0	20004	$-1/(-2^*-3-4^*5)^*(6^*7+8)+9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*8^*7+6+5^*4^3(3^*2)+1$
B6B1	20005	$12+3^*-4^*5^*-6-7+89AB$	$BA98+7^*(-65-4-(-3+2))+1$
B6B2	20006	$-12^*(3-45^*6-(789-A+B))$	$BA+9876+5^*-432^*-1$
B6B3	20007	$123^*(4-5)^*(6+7-8+9-AB)$	$BA-(-9876+5^*-432-1)$
B6B4	20008	$1-2+3^*(4+5)+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5-4-321$
B6B5	20009	$-12-3^*45^*(-6+7)^*(-8-9A)-B$	$B^*(A9+876-5-4+321)$
B6B6	20010	$1^2+3^*(4+5)+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*((-8+7-6^*5)/(4+3)^2+1)$
B6B7	20011	$1^2+3^*(4+5)+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76^*5+43^*-2-1$
B6B8	20012	$1+2+3^*(4+5)+6^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7^*-6+5^*-43^*2^*1$
B6B9	20013	$1-((-2/-3-(4-5^*6)/7-8)^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-76^*5-43^*2+1$
B6BA	20014	$((-1+(-2-3^*4)^*5)^*-6+7)^*8-9+A-B$	$BA-9^*-8^*(76-5+4+3)^*(2+1)$
B6BB	20015	$((1-(2+3+4))^4+5^*6^*7/8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*65-4+3^*-2^*1$
B700	20016	$-1^*-2^*-3^*(-4-5+6)^*(789+A-B)$	$BA98-(76+5)-(-4+321)$
B701	20017	$-1-2^*3^*-4^*(-5+6^*7)^*(8+9)-A^*B$	$B-A-9^*8^*(-7-65^*4+32-1)$
B702	20018	$1+(-2-3^*-4^*(-5^*6+7))^*-8^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-76+5-(4+321)$
B703	20019	$(-1-2^*3)^*-4^*(-5-6)^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7-65-4-321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B704	20020	$-12^*(-3-45-6+7)^*(-89+AB)$	$-B-(-A987-65)-43^*-21$
B705	20021	$(-1+2^*(-3-4)^*5)^*6^*(7^*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+65-432+1$
B706	20022	$1+(2^*3+4)^{\wedge}5/(6+(7-8)^{\wedge}9)+A+B$	$BA^*(98+76-54-(3-2))^*1$
B707	20023	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)^*((-6+7)/8+9)+A+B$	$B+A+9+((8-(7+6+5))^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1$
B708	20024	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+76^*(5-4-3)^*(2+1)$
B709	20025	$-1^*(2+3-4^*-5)^*(6+78^*-9+A+B)$	$BA98-7^*65-4+3-(2+1)$
B70A	20026	$-1^*(-234+5)^*(67-8-9)^*(-A+B)$	$BA98-76+5+4-321$
B70B	20027	$1^{\wedge}2^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(65-4)-321$
B710	20028	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7^*-65+4-3-2^*-1$
B711	20029	$1^*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+65^*(4+3))- (2+1)$
B712	20030	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6-54-321$
B713	20031	$1+(2^*3+4)^{\wedge}5/(6+7-8)+9+A+B$	$BA98+7+6^*5^*(4-(-3+21))$
B714	20032	$-1-(-2+(-3+4-5^{\wedge}6)/7+8)^*9+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7^*6)^*(-5^*4^*3+2)+1$
B715	20033	$-1^*(-23+4)^*(567-8^*-9)^*(-A+B)$	$BA98+7-(-65+432)-1$
B716	20034	$-1^*23^*(-456-78-(9+A-B))$	$BA98+7^*(-6-5)+4-321$
B717	20035	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5+6^*7-8)^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98+76-5-432^*1$
B718	20036	$1-(-2+(-3-(-4+5^{\wedge}6)/7+8)^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98+76-5-432+1$
B719	20037	$-1+(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*65-4^*-3^*(2-1)$
B71A	20038	$(-1^*-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76^*5-43-21$
B71B	20039	$1+(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7^*6-5^*-4^{\wedge}3)+2^{\wedge}1$
B720	20040	$1-2+3^*4^*5^*6^*7^*8-9-A^*B$	$B+A-9^*-8^*(-7^*6-5/-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1$
B721	20041	$-1-234+(-5-678-9)^*(-A-B)$	$BA98-(-7+65-(4-321))$
B722	20042	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)-5/(6-7)^*8)^*9+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-54-321$
B723	20043	$1+2-34^*5+(67+89)^*A^*-B$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}1)$
B724	20044	$-1-2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9)+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+6)-54-321$
B725	20045	$1+(-2-(3-4^{\wedge}5/-6^{\wedge}7))^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98+7^*-6-5^*4-321$
B726	20046	$1-2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+76-(-5+432)+1$
B727	20047	$-1+2+3-(-4-56-78+9)^*AB$	$BA9+8^*-7+6^*5^*(-432+1)$
B728	20048	$12^*(-345-678+9)^*(A-B)$	$-B-A-9^*((-8-7)^*-6^*-5+4)^*(3+2)-1$
B729	20049	$1^*-2-3^*-4^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7^*-65-4^*(-3-(2+1))$
B72A	20050	$1-2-3^*-4^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$-B-(A+9876)-5^*-4321$
B72B	20051	$1+2^*34^*-5^*-67+89^*A^*B$	$-B+A-9^*-87-(6-543)^*21$
B730	20052	$-1^*2^*3^*(4+5-6)^*(-789+A-B)$	$BA98-7+6+5^*43^*-2-1$
B731	20053	$-1^*-2-3^*-4^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$-B+A987+654+321$
B732	20054	$1^{\wedge}2-3^*-4^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8-9)-(A-B)$	$BA98+7^*-6^*5+4^*-3^*21$
B733	20055	$-1-(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6+5^*-43^*2^*1$
B734	20056	$(-1^*-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*7^*8+9+A-B$	$-B-A98^*(-7-6)-5-4^*(32+1)$
B735	20057	$1-(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$-B^*A+(-9-8^*7^*6)^*(-5+4^{\wedge}3+2)^*1$
B736	20058	$(-1+(-2^{\wedge}3^*(-4-5^*6)+7)^*8)^*9-(A+B)$	$BA98+7^*-65-4+32-1$
B737	20059	$-1+(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$-B^*A+(-9^*-8/7+6)^*(-5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$
B738	20060	$((-1-2+3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)/-7+8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*(65-(4+3-2^*1))$
B739	20061	$-1^*23^*(-456-78-9)^*(-A+B)$	$BA98+7^*-65+4^*3^*(2+1)$
B73A	20062	$-12^*(-345-678-(-9-A)-B)$	$BA98-76^*5-43-(2-1)$
B73B	20063	$-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7/8/9+A-B$	$-B-A98-7^*6^*5^*(43^*2+1)$
B740	20064	$(1-2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7/8/9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*6-(5-4+321)$
B741	20065	$1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7/8/9+A-B$	$B+A-9^*(-8+7^*(-6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)))/2+1$
B742	20066	$-1-2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9)+A+B$	$BA98-7-(-6^*-5+4+321)$
B743	20067	$(-1+2-3^*4^*-5^*-6^*-7)^*8+9-A^*B$	$BA98+7+6+5^*43^*-2^*1$
B744	20068	$1-2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9)+A+B$	$-B-A-9^*(8-(7-6-5)^{\wedge}4)/3^{\wedge}2+1$
B745	20069	$(-1+2^*3)^*(-4-5^*-6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9-(8+(-7-6)/-5))^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
B746	20070	$1^*2^*(-34-5^*-6-7^*(-8-9AB))$	$B+A+(-9-8^*7^*-6^*5)^*4^*3-(2+1)$
B747	20071	$1^*-2-3^*-4^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8-9)+A+B$	$BA9+9^*-8^*-7+(-6-543)^*-21$
B748	20072	$1^*(23-45)^*(-67^*8-9-AB)$	$B+A-9876-5^*-4321$
B749	20073	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7^*-65-(-43+2+1)$
B74A	20074	$(-1+2)^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8^*9)-(A-B)$	$BA98+7^*-65-(-43+2)^*1$
B74B	20075	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8^*9)+A-B$	$B-(A987-654-321)$
B750	20076	$1^*(2-3)^*(4+5+678-9)^*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7^*-65+43^*(2-1)$
B751	20077	$-1-(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9)+A+B$	$BA98+7^*(6-54)+3^*(2-1)$
B752	20078	$(-1+(-2^{\wedge}3^*(-4-5^*6)+7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*(6+54+3)+21$
B753	20079	$1-(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9)+A+B$	$BA98-76^*5+4-(32+1)$
B754	20080	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7^*8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98+76^*5+(-4+32)^*-1$
B755	20081	$-1^*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7^*8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98-76+54-321$
B756	20082	$((-1-2+3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)/-7+8)^*9+A+B$	$BA98+76^*5-4-3-21$
B757	20083	$(1+2+3^*4^*5^*6^*7)^*8+9-A^*B$	$BA98+7^*(6-54)-3^*21$
B758	20084	$-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9-(A+B)$	$B+A^*987+65^*(4-3^*-21)$
B759	20085	$-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7/8/9+A+B$	$BA98-7-(6+5+4+321)$
B75A	20086	$1^*(23-4-(567-89^*-A))^*B$	$BA98-7-654+321$
B75B	20087	$12-345^*6^*-7+(-8-9-A)^*B$	$-B+A-9^*(-8-76+5)^*(-4+3+21)$
B760	20088	$-1^*-23^*(456-(7-8)-(9^*-A-B))$	$BA98+7-6^*5-(-4+321)$
B761	20089	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3^*4)^*5-6^*(7^*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8^*(7-(6-5^{\wedge}4)))^*(-3-(2-1))$
B762	20090	$1^*2^*(3-4)^*(5-6)^*7^*(8+9AB)$	$BA98+76^*-5+4-3-21$
B763	20091	$(-1+2^*3)^*(-4-5^*-6^*(7+8))^*9+A+B$	$BA98-7^*-6+5^*(43^*-2-1)$
B764	20092	$-1^*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8^*9)+A+B$	$BA98-765-(-432+1)$
B765	20093	$-1+(-2^*-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8^*9-A-B$	$BA98-7-6-5+4-321$
B766	20094	$-1^*2^*-3^*(-4-5^*-678-9AB)$	$BA98-765+432+1$
B767	20095	$1+23^*456+78^*(9-(A-B))$	$BA98-7-6-(-5+4)-321$
B768	20096	$(-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8)))^*9+A-B$	$B+A987+6+(-5-43)^*-21$
B769	20097	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8^*9)+A+B$	$BA98-(7-6+5-(-4-321))$
B76A	20098	$((-1^*-2/-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/(-8^*9)-A^*B$	$BA98-76^*5+43^*-21$
B76B	20099	$1+((-2/-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/(-8^*9)-A^*B$	$BA98+7-6-5-4-321$
B770	20100	$1^*(2345+67)^*(-89-A^*-B)$	$BA98+7-(654-321)$
B771	20101	$12+34^*5-(678-9)^*(-A-B)$	$BA98+76^*5-4^*-3-21$
B772	20102	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)-5/-6^*7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA9-8+7-6^*5^*(-432+1)$
B773	20103	$(-1-(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}5/6)^*7)^*(8+9)-A^*B$	$BA98-7-6+5+4-321$
B774	20104	$-12^*(-3+4-5-6-7+8-9AB)$	$BA98+76^*5-5-(4+3^*2)^*1$
B775	20105	$-1^*-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-(5-4)-321$
B776	20106	$1^*-2^*(345+67^*8)^*9^*(-A+B)$	$B+A+9-8^*7^*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}1$
B777	20107	$-1+(-2-(-3+4-5^{\wedge}6)/7+8))^*9+A^*B$	$BA98-(7-(6+5-(4+321)))$
B778	20108	$1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6^*(7+8))^*9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9^*(8-(7-6-5)^{\wedge}4)/3^{\wedge}2-1$
B779	20109	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5+6+7+8)^*9+A+B$	$BA98-(7+6)-(-5+4+321)$
B77A	20110	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^*-4^*(5^*6+7))^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-76^*5-4-3+2+1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B77B	20111	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5-6*(7*8+9)+A+B$	$BA98+7*(-6-54)+32-1$
B780	20112	$(-1+2-3*-4*-5*6)*-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*-54+3*-21$
B781	20113	$-1+(-2*-3-4^{\wedge}5*-6^{\wedge}7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+76*-5+(-4+3+2)*-1$
B782	20114	$(-1*-2*-3-4^{\wedge}5*6^{\wedge}7)*-8*9+A-B$	$BA98-76*5+4-(3+2)+1$
B783	20115	$1+(-2*-3-4^{\wedge}5*-6^{\wedge}7)*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-(-5-4+321)$
B784	20116	$(-1+2-3*-4*-5*6)*-7*8-9+A+B$	$BA98-76*5-(4-3-(2+1))$
B785	20117	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6*7*8-9+A*B$	$BA98+7-6+5-(-4+321)$
B786	20118	$12*(345-6)*(7-(-8-9+A*B))$	$BA9-8-(7+6*5*432*-1)$
B787	20119	$-1*(-2-3)*(4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)-8*9)+A-B$	$BA9-8-7-6*5*-432+1$
B788	20120	$1*(2+3)*4*(56+7-8*-9A-B)$	$-B-A-9*((-8+7-6)*-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
B789	20121	$1+(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}5/6)*-7*(8+9)-A*B$	$BA98-(-7-6)+5-(4+321)$
B78A	20122	$(-1/-2+3*4*-5*6)*-7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A-9*((-8+7-6)*-5*-4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
B78B	20123	$1+2*3456+7*(8-9A)*-B$	$-B+A-9*-8*(7+6)/(5*4+3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
B790	20124	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4))-5/-6*7*8)*9+A+B$	$BA98-76*5-(-4-3-2-1)$
B791	20125	$-1234+5*6*7*89+AB$	$-B+A-9-8*-7*-6*5*4*-3-21$
B792	20126	$-1-2*(-3+456)+(7+8)*9AB$	$BA98+76*-5-4*-3*(2-1)$
B793	20127	$-1*-2*(-3-4^{\wedge}5-6*(7+8))*-9+A+B$	$BA98+7*-65+43*2*1$
B794	20128	$-1+234*56-78-9AB$	$BA-9+8*76-543*-21$
B795	20129	$-1-(2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))-(-6*-7+8)*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6+5-(-4+321)$
B796	20130	$1*-2*(3-45+67-8*9A)*B$	$-B*A*(-9-87-65-(-4-3+2-1))$
B797	20131	$1-2-3*(-4*-5*-6*7*8+9)+A-B$	$-B+A9*87-(6+5+4)*-321$
B798	20132	$-12*(34-56+7+8-9AB)$	$BA98+76*-5-4-3+21$
B799	20133	$-1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-76+54)-321$
B79A	20134	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7*8-9+A-B$	$BA9+8-7+6*-5*-432*1$
B79B	20135	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+(-6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6*-54+32*-1$
B7A0	20136	$12345+6*7*-89-AB$	$BA98+7*(6-54)-(-3+21)$
B7A1	20137	$1+(-2*-3-4^{\wedge}5*-6^{\wedge}7)*8*9+A+B$	$-B+A987+6*5*(43-2)-1$
B7A2	20138	$1^{\wedge}2*3^{\wedge}4(4+5)+6*7*8+9A*B$	$BA98+7*-6-54*3*2*-1$
B7A3	20139	$-12-3-4-(5-(678+9))*(A+B)$	$BA98-76*-5*(-4+3)+21$
B7A4	20140	$(-1/-2+3*4*-5*6)*-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6-5-4-321$
B7A5	20141	$((1+2*3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/8+9+A-B$	$-B*(A-(987-6-5)+4-321)$
B7A6	20142	$1*-23*(-456+7-(-8+9+A*B))$	$-B-A98*-7+6+5432+1$
B7A7	20143	$-1-(-2+(-3+4-5^{\wedge}6)/7+8)*9+A*B$	$BA98+76-5*-43*-2-1$
B7A8	20144	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4-5+6))*(7+8*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7*-6*-5*(-4+3)*-2*-1$
B7A9	20145	$((1+2*3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/8-9+A+B$	$BA98+7-6*(54+3*2+1)$
B7AA	20146	$-12*(3-4)*(5+6-7-(-8-9AB))$	$BA+9+8*76+543*21$
B7AB	20147	$-1-2+3*4*5*6*7*8-9+A-B$	$-B-A+9+8*7*6*5*4*3-2+1$
B7B0	20148	$-1*2+3*4*5*6*7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6*5-(-4+321)$
B7B1	20149	$1-2+3*4*5*6*7*8-9+A-B$	$BA9+8+7-6*5*-432+1$
B7B2	20150	$-1*(2^{\wedge}3+4)*-5*-6*-7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6*54-32+1$
B7B3	20151	$1^{\wedge}2+3*4*5*6*7*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*5*(4+3)*-2*-1$
B7B4	20152	$1*(-2+345+67+89A)*B$	$B-(A+9-8*76*(5+4)*(3+21))$
B7B5	20153	$1+2+3*4*5*6*7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A98*(7+6)-54-(-3+21)$
B7B6	20154	$(-1/-2+3*-4*-5*6*7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6*(54+3)-2+1$
B7B7	20155	$1-(2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))-6*(7+8*9))+A-B$	$B-A98-765*-4*(3+2)*1$
B7B8	20156	$(-1*(-2/-3-(4-5^{\wedge}6))/(-7+8)*9+A-B$	$B-A98*-7+6*-543*-2+1$
B7B9	20157	$12345-6*-7*-89-A*B$	$B+A-9-8*7*6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
B7BA	20158	$-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)*5/(6/7-8/9)+A-B$	$BA98-7-6+54-321$
B7BB	20159	$1^{\wedge}2/3*4*5*6*7*8*9+A-B$	$BA9-8*7-6*5*(432-1)$
B800	20160	$-12*-34*(5*6+7-(-8+9))*(A+B)$	$-B-A-9*-8*7-(6+((-5-4)*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
B801	20161	$1*2+((-3+4-5^{\wedge}6))/(-7+8)*9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6*5-432+1$
B802	20162	$-1+2*3*-4*(-567+8)+9*AB$	$BA9-(8-7)-6*-5*(432+1)$
B803	20163	$((1+2*3+4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)/8+9+A+B$	$B+A+9*(8*7*6*5*4/3-2)^{\wedge}1$
B804	20164	$1-2345+(67+89)*AB$	$BA*(98+7+6+54-(32-1))$
B805	20165	$1+2*-3*45-(-6-78)*(9-A)*-B$	$BA98-(-7+6*54)-(-3+21)$
B806	20166	$-1*2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6+5*4*(-3+21)$
B807	20167	$1-2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*(-54-3)-2*1$
B808	20168	$((1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5*-6^{\wedge}7/8)/9+A-B$	$-B+A987+6*5*(43-2+1)$
B809	20169	$1^{\wedge}2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5+4*-3*21$
B80A	20170	$1*2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6+54-321$
B80B	20171	$1+2+3*4*5*6*7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6+5*(-43-21)$
B810	20172	$(-1/-2+3*-4*-5*6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-(-6+54)+321)$
B811	20173	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+(6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+65-4-321$
B812	20174	$12*(34+56-(78-9AB))$	$BA98-7-65*4-3*21$
B813	20175	$1+2*(3-(-4-(5-6))-(-78+9)))*-AB$	$BA98-7-6*54+3-2+1$
B814	20176	$-1*(23-4-567)*(-89+AB)$	$-BA-9*-876-5*4*-321$
B815	20177	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(-6*-54-3-2+1)$
B816	20178	$123*(4+56-78-(-9-AB))$	$-B+A98*(7+6)-(-5-4)+32*-1$
B817	20179	$1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6*-54-3*-2*1$
B818	20180	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-(7+65-4*-3*21)$
B819	20181	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*-54-3*-2*-1$
B81A	20182	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*5*4/3+2-1$
B81B	20183	$1-2-(3+45-(67+89))*-A*-B$	$B+A+9*8*7*6*5*4/3+2/1$
B820	20184	$-1*(-2-3*-4*-5*6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6+54-321$
B821	20185	$1-2*-34*5*6*7+8*-9AB$	$B*(A+9-87+6*-54*(-3-2)-1)$
B822	20186	$(-1-2*3-4^{\wedge}5*6^{\wedge}7)*-8*9+A-B$	$B-A-(-9+8*(-76-54*-32*-1))$
B823	20187	$1^{\wedge}2-3*(-4*-5*-6*7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+65-4-321$
B824	20188	$1*2-3*(-4*-5*-6*7*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+76-5-4-321$
B825	20189	$-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9+8*7*6*5*4*3-2+1$
B826	20190	$-1+23+4+(5+67)*-8*(-9-(A+B))$	$BA98-76*5+43+21$
B827	20191	$-12+34*5*6-(-7-8)*9AB$	$B-A98*(-7-6)+5-43-2*1$
B828	20192	$(1+2+3*4*5*6*7)*8+9+A-B$	$BA98+7+6*-54+3*2-1$
B829	20193	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA-9876-5*-4321$
B82A	20194	$1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7-65+4*-3*21$
B82B	20195	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A-B$	$BA98+7+65+4-321$
B830	20196	$1*-23*(456-78-9A*B)$	$BA98+76-5+4-321$
B831	20197	$-1+2*3*-4*(-5+6+78)*-9-A*-B$	$BA98-76*(-5+4)-321$
B832	20198	$(-1/-2+3*-4*-5*6)*7*8+9-(A-B)$	$BA98+76-(-5+4+321)$
B833	20199	$1-(2-34)-(-5-6-7)*-8*(-9-AB)$	$-B+A987+6*-5*-43+2-1$
B834	20200	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7*8*9+A+B$	$BA98+7*(-65+43)*-2*-1$
B835	20201	$12+3*(4567+8-9A*B)$	$-B+A-9+87+(-6-5)*-4*321$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B836	20202	$-12^*-3^*(-456-7^*8-9^*-AB)$	$BA98-7^*6^*5+4^*-32^*1$
B837	20203	$-123+4+(5-(-678-9))^*(A+B)$	$-B-(-A987+6-543^*2)-1$
B838	20204	$1-2-34+5+(67+89)^*A^*B$	$B+A+(9+8+7)^*(6+5^*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
B839	20205	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7^*8^*9+A+B$	$B+A+(9+8+7)^*(6+5^*4+3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
B83A	20206	$(-1+2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98+76+5+4-321$
B83B	20207	$1-234^*-56-7-8-9AB$	$B^*(A9-(-8-765)-(-432-1))$
B840	20208	$1+2-3^*(-4567-8^*(9-AB))$	$BA98-7-6^*(5+43+2)-1$
B841	20209	$((-1^*-2/-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6^{\wedge}7/((-8^*9)-(A-B))$	$BA98+7-(-6^*-54+3)+21$
B842	20210	$1+((-2/-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6^{\wedge}7/((-8^*9)-(A-B))$	$-BA+9^*87+(6+543)^*21$
B843	20211	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5-(-6-(-7-8)^*9))+A-B$	$BA98-(7-6^*-54-32^*1)$
B844	20212	$(-1-(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}5/6)^*7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*-54+32+1$
B845	20213	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-5^*(-6+7^*8)^*9)+A-B$	$BA98+7^*6+5+4-321$
B846	20214	$1234+5-(678^*(-9-A)+B)$	$-B-A98^*(7+6)^*(-5+4)-3^*(2-1)$
B847	20215	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7^*8^*9+A+B$	$-B+A987+6-(543^*-2+1)$
B848	20216	$-1^*(-2+34)^*(-5^*67-8-9A-B)$	$BA98-76^*5+43^*-2^*-1$
B849	20217	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7^*8^*9+A+B$	$BA98+76-5^*-4-321$
B84A	20218	$1^*-2^*(-3-45+678-(-9-A))^*-B$	$B^*-A+(-9^*-8^*(-7^*-6+5)+4)^*(3+2+1)$
B84B	20219	$-1+234^*56-(-7+8+9AB)$	$BA98-76-5^*43^*(2-1)$
B850	20220	$-1^{\wedge}2^*-3^{\wedge}4^*-5^*(6-7^*8)-9-A-B$	$-B-A-9+(8+7-6^*5)^{\wedge}4/(3/2+1)$
B851	20221	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)^*-8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98-76-5^*43+2^*1$
B852	20222	$1+234^*56^*(-7+8)-9AB$	$BA98+7-6^*(5^*-4^*-3-2)-1$
B853	20223	$-1^*(-23-(4+56+78))^*(9A-B)$	$B+A987-6^*-5^*43+2+1$
B854	20224	$-1-(-2-3)-(4^*5-(67+89)^*A^*B)$	$BA98+7-6^*54+32-1$
B855	20225	$-12+345^*-6^*7^*(8-9)-AB$	$B+A987-(6+543^*-2)-1$
B856	20226	$-1+234^*56+7^*(8^*-9-AB)$	$BA98-(-7-6^*-54)-(-32-1)$
B857	20227	$1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5^{\wedge}6+7^*8^*9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9+8-7+(6+5)^*4^*321$
B858	20228	$-1+(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}5/6)^*-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$-B-A+9/(8+7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)/3^*2-1$
B859	20229	$(-1+2^*3)^*(-4-5^*6)^*-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-76-5^*(-43+2)^*-1$
B85A	20230	$1+(-2/-3-4^{\wedge}5/6)^*-7^*(8+9)+A-B$	$B+A987+65^*-4^*(-3-2)^*1$
B85B	20231	$-1/-2^*(-3^*-4)^{\wedge}5/6-7^*8^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-6+54^*(-3-2)^*1$
B860	20232	NA	$BA98-(-7+6^*(5+43)+2)-1$
B861	20233	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5-(-6-(-7-8)^*9))+A+B$	$-B-A+9+8^*-7^*(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
B862	20234	$-1+2+345^*-6^*-7-8-9A-B$	$BA98-76-5^*(43-(2+1))$
B863	20235	$-1-234^*-56-7+8-9AB$	$B+A+(-9^*(-8-7^*6)^*-5+4)^*-3^*(2+1)$
B864	20236	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*-4))^*5+6+(-7-8)^*9-A^*B$	$BA9+87+6^*-5^*432^*-1$
B865	20237	$-1+2-3+4-5+(-67-89)^*A^*-B$	$BA9+87-6^*5^*-432+1$
B866	20238	$(1-2^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}5^*6^*7)/(-8-9)+A-B$	$B+A987+6-543^*2^*-1$
B867	20239	$(-1+2^*3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^*-7^*-8^*9)+A-B$	$B-(-A987-6)-(-543^*2-1)$
B868	20240	$1^*-2^*-34^*(5+6-7-(8+9A))^*-B$	$B^*-A^*(-98+7+6-(5+43+21))$
B869	20241	$-1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-65^*-4-3)-21$
B86A	20242	$1^*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7^*6-5^*43-21$
B86B	20243	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-65^*4-3-2-1$
B870	20244	$-12^*(3+4+56-78-9AB)$	$BA98-76+5^*-43+21$
B871	20245	$-1+2^*3-4^*(-56+7+89)^*A^*-B$	$BA98+7-6+54^*(-3-2)^*1$
B872	20246	$12345+6^*7^*-89-(A+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-8^*7^*(6-(-5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
B873	20247	$-123-4^*5^*-678+9A^*B$	$-B-A+(9-8-7)^*((-6-5-4)^{\wedge}3-(2+1))$
B874	20248	$-1+2^*(-3+4^{\wedge}5-(-6-7)^*8)^*9+A-B$	$BA9-8^*-7^*6^*54+321$
B875	20249	$((1^*2+3)^*4+5)^*(6^*(7+8)^*9+A-B)$	$BA98-7+65^*-4+3-2-1$
B876	20250	$1^*23^*(456-7+8+9A-B)$	$B+A+(-9-8)^*-7^*(-6^*-5+4)^*(3+2)-1$
B877	20251	$(-1+2^*3)^*(-4-5^*6)^*-7^*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B^*(A+9-876-5-432+1)$
B878	20252	$1+2^*(-3+4^{\wedge}5-(-6-7)^*8)^*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-7^*(6+5)^*4-(3+2-1)$
B879	20253	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*-4))^*5+(-6-7)^*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-7^*6^*5+43^*-2+1$
B87A	20254	$(-1+(-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*-7)^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-65^*-4-3)^*2^*1$
B87B	20255	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4-5+6))^*(7+8^*9)+A^*B$	$BA98+7^*6+(5+4)^*(-32-1)$
B880	20256	$(-1^*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}5-6^*7-8^*9-A^*B$	$BA98+7^*-6-5^*(43+2)-1$
B881	20257	$-1+234^*56-78+9A^*B$	$BA98-76+54^*-3-21$
B882	20258	$-1^{\wedge}2^*-3^{\wedge}4^*-5^*(6-7^*8)+9+A-B$	$BA-(-9+8)+7-(-6-5)^*4^*321$
B883	20259	$1+(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5^*(4+32+1)$
B884	20260	$(1-2^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}5^*6^*7)/(-8-9)+A+B$	$BA98+7-6-5+4^*3^*-21$
B885	20261	$-1-23^*(4-567)-(-8+9AB)$	$BA98+76+54-321$
B886	20262	$-1^*(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76^*5-4^*(-32+1)$
B887	20263	$1+(-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*-7^*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6^*(5-43-2-1)$
B888	20264	$1^*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$-BA-9-8+7-654^*(3-21)$
B889	20265	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7^*8)^*9+A+B$	$BA98-(-7-65^*-4-3+2-1)$
B88A	20266	$-1-(2^{\wedge}3+4)^*(-5^*-6^*-7^*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+76^*-5-4^*32^*-1$
B88B	20267	$12345+6^*-7^*89^*(-A+B)$	$BA98+7+65^*-4-(-3-2)-1$
B890	20268	$1+2-345^*-6^*7-89^*(-A+B)$	$B+A+8^*-76+543^*21$
B891	20269	$1+2-345^*-6^*7-89-(A-B)$	$BA98+7+65^*-4+3+2+1$
B892	20270	$1+234^*56+7^*(-8+9^*(-A-B))$	$BA98+7^*(-65-(4-32-1))$
B893	20271	$-1-23-4^*-5^*678+9^*AB$	$BA98-7-6-5^*43-21$
B894	20272	$12^*(3-45+67-8+9AB)$	$-B-A-(98+7+654^*(3-21))$
B895	20273	$(-1^*-2-3^*-4^*5)^*(-6^*-7^*8-9)+A-B$	$B^*(-A+9)^*(-87+6)^*(-5-4+3+21)$
B896	20274	$(-1+(-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*-7)^*8+9-(A-B)$	$-BA+98^*(76+54-(3-21))$
B897	20275	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*-4))^*5+(-6-7)^*(8+9)+A+B$	$B+A+9+8^*-7^*(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
B898	20276	$(-1-2^*(-3^*(-4-5)^*-6^*-7-8))^*-9+A-B$	$BA98-76-(-5-4)^*(3-21)$
B899	20277	$((-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*-4^{\wedge}5-6^*7)^*(8+9)-(A+B)$	$B+A-9^*(-87-6)-543^*-21$
B89A	20278	$1+234^*56+7^*8-9AB$	$B+A+(-9+8^*7)^*((-6^*(-5+4))^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
B89B	20279	$-1-((-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-(76-54^*-3)-2-1$
B8A0	20280	$12+345+(-67+8^*-9)^*-AB$	$-BA-(9-8-7+654^*(3-21))$
B8A1	20281	$1-((-2-3^*-4^*-5^*6)^*7^*8-9)+A-B$	$B+A98^*(7+6)+54+3-21$
B8A2	20282	$-12-3-4^*5^*-678+9^*AB$	$BA98-76+54^*-3^*(2-1)$
B8A3	20283	$-1-234^*-5-67^*(-89-AB)$	$BA98-(-7-6)-(5^*43+21)$
B8A4	20284	$-1^*(-2-3^*-4^*5^*6)^*7^*8-9+A+B$	$BA98-76-54^*3+2^*1$
B8A5	20285	$1+2-3-4^*-5+(678+9)^*(A+B)$	$BA98-(76-54^*-3-2-1)$
B8A6	20286	$-12^*(-345-678-(9+A-B))$	$-B-A-98+7-654^*(3-21)$
B8A7	20287	$(-1+2)^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*-7^*(8+9)-A^*B$	$BA98-7+65^*-4+32^*1$
B8A8	20288	$12345+6^*-7^*89+A+B$	$BA98-(-7-65^*-4)-(-32-1)$
B8A9	20289	$(-1^*-2^{\wedge}3+4)^*(-5^*-6^*7^*8+9)+A+B$	$B+A+(9-8-7)^*((-6-5-4)^{\wedge}3-(2+1))$
B8AA	20290	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3^*4)^*5+(-6-(7+8))^*9+A-B$	$-BA+9^*876-5432^*-1$
B8AB	20291	$(-1+2^*3)^*(4+5^*-6^*(-7-8)^*9)+A+B$	$BA98+7^*(6+5-43+2-1)$
B8B0	20292	$1+2+3^*4^*(5^*6^*7^*8+9)+A+B$	$-B+A-98-7-654^*(3-21)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B8B1	20293	$-1+23*(-4+567)+8+9*-AB$	$-B*-A+(9+8+7)*(6+5*4+3)^2-1$
B8B2	20294	$12+3*-4*5*(-6-7)*(-89+AB)$	$BA98-76+5*4*3*(-2-1)$
B8B3	20295	$(-1*-2-3*-4*5)*(-6*-7*8-9)+A+B$	$BA98-7-6+5*-43-2+1$
B8B4	20296	$-1-2*(3+(-4^5-(-6-7)*8)*9)+A-B$	$B+A+(-9-8*-7*6)*(-5*-4*3+2)+1$
B8B5	20297	$1-2-345*-6*7-8*9*(-A+B)$	$-B-A-9*-876+5*4*321$
B8B6	20298	$1-2*(3+(-4^5+(-6-7)*8)*9)+A-B$	$B-A98*(-7-6)+54-3-2*1$
B8B7	20299	$((-1-2^3)*-4^5-6*7*(8+9)-(-A-B))$	$-BA-9*-87*-6*-5-4321$
B8B8	20300	$12-345*-6*7-(89-A-B)$	$BA98+7-65*4+32-1$
B8B9	20301	$-1-((-2-3*-4*-5*6)*7*8-9)+A+B$	$BA98+7+6*5*(-4+3*-2+1)$
B8BA	20302	$1+23+4+5+(-678-9)*(-A-B)$	$BA98+7-65*4+32+1$
B8BB	20303	$(-1-2*(-3-4*5)*6+7)*8*9+A-B$	$B+A+9-8*-7*(-6*-5*4*3+2)+1$
B900	20304	$1*23*-4*(5-(-6+78+9A)+B)$	$-B-A-(-9-87+654-3)*-21$
B901	20305	$1*2+3*(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A*B$	$BA98-7+6+5*-43-2-1$
B902	20306	$1+2+3*(4+5)+6+7*8*9+A*B$	$-BA*(-98-(7-6+54-32*1))$
B903	20307	$1*(2+3)^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+6-5*-43-(-2-1))$
B904	20308	$1+(2+3)^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A-B$	$BA98-(7-6-5*-43*(2-1))$
B905	20309	$-1*(-2/3-4^5/-6*-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$BA98+7-6-5*43-2+1$
B906	20310	$1-(-2/3-4^5/-6*-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$BA98-(7-6+5*43-2*1)$
B907	20311	$-12-34*56-(7+8)*9*AB$	$BA98-7-6+5*(-43+2+1)$
B908	20312	$((1-2^3)^4+(-5-(6+7))*8)*9+A-B$	$-BA-98+(-7-654)*(3-21)$
B909	20313	NA	$BA98+7-6*(-5+43-2-1)$
B90A	20314	$-12*(-34-5+6+7+8-9AB)$	$B*-A+9-(-8-7*-6^5/-4*3)/2-1$
B90B	20315	$123-4*(-5-6+7)*(89A-B)$	$-B-A98+7*6*(54+321)$
B910	20316	$((1+2)^3*4*(-5-6)+7)*(8+9)-(-A-B)$	$BA98-76-5-43*(2+1)$
B911	20317	$(-1+2-3*-4*5*6)*7*8-9+A*B$	$-B+A-9*-876-5*4*-321$
B912	20318	$(-1/-2-3*-4*5)*-6*-7*8-9+A-B$	$B+A9*-8*(-7+6)-543*-21$
B913	20319	$-1+23+45-(-67-89)*A*B$	$BA98+7*(-65+4+32)*1$
B914	20320	$1*2*3*4*(5+6+7+89+AB)$	$BA98+7-6-5*(-43+2)*-1$
B915	20321	$12+34*(-56+7)*-8+9AB$	$BA98+7*-6+(-54-3)*(2+1)$
B916	20322	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6*(7-(8-9))-A*B$	$BA98-7+6*-5*(4+3)-21$
B917	20323	$((-1+2^3*(-3*-4))*-5-6*7*(8-9))-A*B$	$B-A-98-7*6*(5-4-321)$
B918	20324	$(-1-2^3)*(-4-5*(-6+7*8)*9)+A*B$	$BA98-7-65*4+3*21$
B919	20325	$(-1-2*(-3-4*5)*6+7)*8*9+A+B$	$BA98-7*65+4*-3*-21$
B91A	20326	$-1-2*-3*(4+(-5-6*7)*-8*9)+A-B$	$BA98-7*-6-5*43-21$
B91B	20327	$(-1-2/-3*-4)*(-5-6)*-7*-8*9+A-B$	$BA98-76+5+4*-32*1$
B920	20328	$1*2*3*4*(-5+6)*-7*(8-9A-B)$	$BA98-76-(-5+4*32)+1$
B921	20329	$1*(2+3)^4+(5/(6-7)+8)^9+A+B$	$BA98-7-65-4*32+1$
B922	20330	$-12+345*-6*-7+89-AB$	$BA98-7*6-54*3*(-2+1)$
B923	20331	$1*-23*(-456-(7+89)-A+B)$	$BA98-7*(6+5)*4+3*21$
B924	20332	$(-1-2^3*4-5*6^7)*-8*9-(-A-B)$	$-B-A9-(-8*7+654*(3-21))$
B925	20333	$(-1-2)*(-3-4*-5*-6*7)*8-9+A*B$	$BA98-(7-6-5*-43-21)$
B926	20334	$-1+234*56-7-8+9A*-B$	$BA98-7+65+4*-3*21$
B927	20335	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6*(7+8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-76-54-3*21$
B928	20336	$-1*234*(5*-6*7+8+9+AB)$	$-B-A+(-9+8*7*6)*(5-4^3)+2/1$
B929	20337	$1-234*(56-7-(-8+9A+B))$	$-B-A+(-9-8*7*6)*(5-4^3)+2+1$
B92A	20338	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6*(-7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7+65*4+3*-21)$
B92B	20339	$(-1-2^3)*-4*-5*(6-7*(8+9))+A-B$	$B*(-A+9-(-876-(-5+432-1)))$
B930	20340	$1-(-2*-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7*(6-5)*(4+3+21)$
B931	20341	$(1^A-2+3)^4*5*(-6-(7+8+9))+A+B$	$BA98-7-6*(5+4)*(3+2-1)$
B932	20342	$-12*(-345-678+9-(-A+B))$	$BA98-(-7+65-4*32*-1)$
B933	20343	NA	$BA98+7-(65+4*32-1)$
B934	20344	NA	$BA-9+87-(-6-5)*-4*-321$
B935	20345	$-1+2-345*-6*7+89-AB$	$-B-A-9*8-7*6+5*4^4(3+2+1)$
B936	20346	$-1-2*-3*-4*-567-(8+9*-AB)$	$BA98-7+6+54*-3-21$
B937	20347	$(-1+2^3*(-3*-4))*5+6+(-7-8)*9-(-A-B)$	$BA98+7-(-6-5*-43)+21$
B938	20348	$(-1+2-3-4^5)/-6*-7*(-8-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7-6+54*-3-21$
B939	20349	$-123*(4-5+6-(-7-(-8+9)*-AB))$	$BA98-(-7-6*(5-4-32)*1)$
B93A	20350	$-1+234*56-7-(-8+9A*B)$	$-B*A*(-98-76-(5-43)-21)$
B93B	20351	$1+234*56+(7-8)*9A*B$	$B-(-A9-87-(6+5)*-4*-321)$
B940	20352	$-1*2*-3*45*(-6+7)*8*(9-(-A+B))$	$BA98+7*-6*5+4+3*-2*1$
B941	20353	$1+2*-3*45*(-6+7)*-8*(9A+B)$	$-B+A+(-9-8*7*6)*(5-4^3)-(-2-1)$
B942	20354	$(-1+2^3+4)^5*(6*-7*8+9)+A-B$	$B+A9*(-8-7)-6543*2*-1$
B943	20355	$-1+2+345*-6*-7-8-9-A+B$	$BA98+7-6*(54-3-21)$
B944	20356	$12-34+(56+78)*(9A+B)$	$BA98+7*-6*5*(4-3)+2*1$
B945	20357	$-1*2*(-3-4^5+(-6-7)*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-(76+5)+4*(-3-21)$
B946	20358	$-1*23*(4*(-56-78)-(-9+AB))$	$B+A+9+8*7*(6*5*4*3+2+1)$
B947	20359	$-1+234*56-7-(89A+B)$	$BA98+76+5+4*3*-21$
B948	20360	$1+(-2*(-3+4^5)+6)*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	$BA98+7-6-5*(4-(-32+1))$
B949	20361	$(-1+2^3*(-3*-4))*5+(-6-7)*8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7*-6+5*(43-2)*-1$
B94A	20362	$1-(-2*-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	$BA98-76+(5+43)*2*-1$
B94B	20363	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6-(-7+8)*9+A*B$	$-B-A+(-9*-8-7*6^5)/-4*3/2-1$
B950	20364	$(-1+2^3*-4^5/-6)*(-7+8)*9-A*B$	$-B-A+(-9*-8-7*6^5)/-4*-3/-2*1$
B951	20365	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6*7-8*9+A-B$	$-B-A+(-9*-8-7*6^5)/-4*3/2+1$
B952	20366	$-1+2+345*-6*-7+89+A*-B$	$BA98-76-(5-43*2)-1$
B953	20367	$-1*(-2-3-4-5*6*7)*(-8-9-A*-B)$	$BA98-76-5-43*2*1$
B954	20368	$1-2^3*(4-5*(6-7*8*9))+A-B$	$BA98-7-65-4*(3+21)$
B955	20369	$1-2-345*(67-(-8+9A+B))$	$-B-A-9*(-8-7*-6^5/4)*3/2-1$
B956	20370	$1*(-2-34)*5*(6-7*8*(-9+AB))$	$BA9-87*6+543*21$
B957	20371	$-1+2-345*(6-(-78+9)-AB)$	$BA98-76-54-32-1$
B958	20372	$(-1*2^3)^4*5+6+(-7-8)*9+A+B$	$BA98-76+(54+32)*-1$
B959	20373	$-1+2+345+(-678+9)*(-A-B)$	$BA98-76-(54+32-1)$
B95A	20374	$1*(23-(-45-67)+8)*(-9+AB)$	$BA98-76-5*4*(3+2)*1$
B95B	20375	$1+234*56+7-89A-B$	$BA98-7-6*5+4*32*-1$
B960	20376	$-1-234*-56-78-9*AB$	$B+A*-98+(76+543)*21$
B961	20377	$((1+2)^3+4^5(5+6-7))*8*9-(-A-B)$	$-B-(A9-876)-543*-21$
B962	20378	$-1+23*(456-(-7-89))-(-A-B)$	$BA98-7-65-43*2*1$
B963	20379	$-1*2*(-3-4^5+(-6-7)*8)*9+A+B$	$BA98-7-65-43*2+1$
B964	20380	$(-1*2^3)^4*5-6*(7+8)-9+A-B$	$BA98+7*6*-5+43-21$
B965	20381	$(-1-2*3^4+5)*(-6-(-7-8)*-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+(-6+5-4)*32*1$
B966	20382	$-12-345*-6*7-89+AB$	$BA98-(76+54-(-3-21))$
B967	20383	$1-234*-56-(7+89A-B)$	$BA98+76*(5-4-3)-(-2-1)$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
B968	20384	$12+345*(-67-8+9A+B)$	$BA98+7-(-6-54*-3+2)+1$
B969	20385	$-1*23*(-456-7-89+A-B)$	$BA98-7*(65-43)-(-2-1)$
B96A	20386	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+(-6-7)*8+9-(A-B)$	$-B+A9*8+76-543*-21$
B96B	20387	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7-8*9+A+B$	$BA-9-8+(7-654)*(3-21)$
B970	20388	$-1-(-2-345*-6*-7)-(8+9)*(A-B)$	$BA98-76-54+3-21$
B971	20389	$12-345*6*-7-89-A*-B$	$BA98-7-6*(-5+4)*(-3-21)$
B972	20390	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5*(6-7*-8*9))+A+B$	$BA98-76-(5+4)+3*-21$
B973	20391	$(1+2^{\wedge}3/4)^{\wedge}5/6*7*8*9-A-B$	$BA98+7-6*5*(4+3-2+1)$
B974	20392	$1+(2-3+4)^{\wedge}5/6*7*8*9-(A+B)$	$BA98+7-65-43*-2*-1$
B975	20393	$-1-2-345*6*-7-89+AB$	$BA98-(76+5)-(-43+21)$
B976	20394	$-1*2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-7-6-5-4*32*1$
B977	20395	$-1+234*56+7-89A+B$	$B-A*9*-87+6543-21$
B978	20396	$-12+34*567+89*-A*B$	$BA98+7*6*5*(4-32*-1)$
B979	20397	$-1+2-345*6*-7-89+AB$	$BA98-7*-6*-5-(-4-32-1)$
B97A	20398	$-12*(3+45-(-6+78+9AB))$	$-B-A*-9*87+6543*(2-1)$
B97B	20399	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98+76+5*43*(-2+1)$
B980	20400	$1*2*(-3-456-78*-9A-B)$	$BA98+76*5+432*-1$
B981	20401	$-12-3-4*-5*678-9A*-B$	$BA98+76*5-432+1$
B982	20402	$1/2*(3-4-5)^{\wedge}6*7/8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7*6*5-(-43+2)-1$
B983	20403	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6-(-7-8)*-9)+A+B$	$BA98-7-65*(4-3+2-1)$
B984	20404	$((-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7-8)+9-A*B$	$BA98-7-65-43-21$
B985	20405	$1-234*-56-789-AB$	$BA98-76-54-3-2*1$
B986	20406	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5+6-(7+8*9)+A-B$	$BA98-(76-(-54-3))-2+1$
B987	20407	$(-1+2*3)/4^{\wedge}(-5+6-7)-8*9+A-B$	$BA98-(-7-6-5-(-4-3))*21$
B988	20408	$1*2*(34+5-((6-78)*9A-B))$	$BA98-76-54-3+2-1$
B989	20409	$-1*(2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))-6*7*(8/9)+A-B$	$BA98-76-(54+3+2*-1)$
B98A	20410	$123+4-5+(67+89)*A*B$	$BA98-76-54+3-2-1$
B98B	20411	$-1+2-34*-567-89*-A*-B$	$BA98-76-54-(-3+2*1)$
B990	20412	$-1*-23*(456-(7+8)+9A+B)$	$-B-A+9*876+5432+1$
B991	20413	$(1+2^{\wedge}3/4)^{\wedge}5/6*7*8*9-(A-B)$	$B+A-9-((-8-7*-6^{\wedge}5/4)*-3/2-1)$
B992	20414	$1+(2-3+4)^{\wedge}5/6*7*8*9-(A-B)$	$BA98-76-54+3+2-1$
B993	20415	$-12-345*-6*7-8*9+AB$	$BA98-76-(5+43+2)-1$
B994	20416	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6)/(7*8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-(76+54-3*2*1)$
B995	20417	$1-(-2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))-6*-7*(8+9)+A+B$	$BA98-(76-(-54+3*2)))+1$
B996	20418	$1+2-3+4*-5*-678+9A*B$	$BA98+7-65-(43+21)$
B997	20419	$((-1+2-3)*4^{\wedge}5+6)*(7-8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-(76-5*4)+3*-21$
B998	20420	$1/2*(3-4-5)^{\wedge}6*7/8+9+A-B$	$BA98-76-5-(43-2*1)$
B999	20421	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*-7*(8+9)+A+B$	$-B-(-A-(-9+8+7))+654*(-3+21)$
B99A	20422	$-1+2+3-4*5*-678-9A*-B$	$BA98-(-7-65*4+321)$
B99B	20423	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*(7+8-9)-(A+B)$	$BA98+7-65+4-3*21$
B9A0	20424	$12-34*-567-89*-A*-B$	$BA98-7+6-54+3*-21$
B9A1	20425	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6/(7-8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-76+5-43-2-1$
B9A2	20426	$1+234*56-789+A*-B$	$BA98-76-5*4-3-21$
B9A3	20427	$-1*-2*(3-4*-5*(6-7*-8*9))+A+B$	$BA98-76+5-43-(2-1)$
B9A4	20428	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5+6-(7+8*9)+A+B$	$BA98-7-65-43-2+1$
B9A5	20429	$(1*2+3)*(4+5*6*(7+8))*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-65-43*(2-1)$
B9A6	20430	$-1+2-(-345*6*7-8*-9)+AB$	$-B+A-9*-876+5432-1$
B9A7	20431	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*(7-(8-9))+A-B$	$BA98-76-(-5-(-43+2+1))$
B9A8	20432	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5-6*7*(8-9)+A-B)$	$BA98-7-(65+43-(2+1))$
B9A9	20433	$(1+2^{\wedge}3/4)^{\wedge}5/6*7*8*9+A+B$	$BA98-(7+6*-5*-4)-(-3-(-2+1))$
B9AA	20434	$-1+2*3*-4*-567+89A-B$	$BA98-76-5+4-32-1$
B9AB	20435	$12+3+4*5*678+9A*B$	$BA98-76-5+4+32*-1$
B9B0	20436	$1+2+3*-45*6*-7+89*AB$	$BA98-76+5-(4+32+1)$
B9B1	20437	$123-4+5-(-678-9)*(A+B)$	$BA98-76-5*(4+3)-2*1$
B9B2	20438	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-7*8+9+A-B$	$BA98-(76-5+4)-32+1$
B9B3	20439	$1/((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7)^{\wedge}(8-9)-(A-B)$	$B+A*9*(-8-76)+54*321$
B9B4	20440	$1*2*(-3-4-56)*(7-8)*(9+AB)$	$BA98-7-6*5*4-3*(-2+1)$
B9B5	20441	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5+6*-7+8-9+A-B$	$BA98+7-65-43-2*1$
B9B6	20442	$1/2*(3-4-5)^{\wedge}6*7/8+9+A+B$	$BA98+7-(65+43+2-1)$
B9B7	20443	$1-234*-56+78-9A*B$	$BA98-(76+5-(-43+21))$
B9B8	20444	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6/(7-8)-9-A-B$	$BA98-(7+65)+4*-3*(2+1)$
B9B9	20445	$-1-234+567*(-89+AB)$	$BA98-76+5+4-32*1$
B9BA	20446	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(-5*(-6*7+8)-9)+A-B$	$BA98+7-65-43-(-2-1)$
B9BB	20447	$1-234+567*(-89+AB)$	$BA98-76-(54-(32-1))$
BA00	20448	$-1-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}5*6)*(-7-8)/9-(A+B)$	$BA*-9*(-8-7+6+5)*-4*(3-2)*-1$
BA01	20449	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6*7-8*9+A-B$	$-B*(-A98+76+54-321)$
BA02	20450	$(-1+(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5)/-6*7*(8+9)+A-B)$	$BA98-7-(6+54+32)+1$
BA03	20451	$(1*2+3)*(4+5*6*(7+8))*9+A+B$	$BA98-76-5+4+3-21$
BA04	20452	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5-6*(-7+8)*9+A+B$	$B+A+9*876-(-5432+1)$
BA05	20453	$-1-(-2-3)-4*5*(-67-8*9A)-B$	$BA98-(76-5-(-4+3))+21$
BA06	20454	$12*(-345+678-9*A*-B)$	$BA98-(7+65+43-21)$
BA07	20455	$-12+345*6*7-8+9A-B$	$BA98-7+6-5-43*2-1$
BA08	20456	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5*6+7*8)*9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(65-4*-3*2*1)$
BA09	20457	$1+2+345*6*7+89-A-B$	$BA98+7-(6+5+43*2)-1$
BA0A	20458	$(-1/2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7+8-9+A+B$	$BA98+7*-6-54-(-3+2+1)$
BA0B	20459	$-1-2*-3*4-(-5+67+8*9)*-AB$	$BA98-7-6-54-3-21$
BA10	20460	$1*-2*(3-4)*56*(7-(-8-9)+AB)$	$BA98-7+6-54-(32+1)$
BA11	20461	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-(7+8+9)+A-B$	$B-A9*-8-7*(-6-543)*-21$
BA12	20462	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6-7)-8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7+6-54-(32-1)$
BA13	20463	$1+2*3+(-56-78)*(-9A-B)$	$BA98+7-6-54+32*-1$
BA14	20464	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6/(7-8)-9+A-B$	$BA98-76+5*(-4+3)*-2*-1$
BA15	20465	$12-3*(4+567)*-8+9*AB$	$BA98-76-5-4+3-2-1$
BA16	20466	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+(6+7)/(8-9)+A-B$	$BA98-76+5-(-4*3+21)$
BA17	20467	$-1*(-2^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}5)/-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	$BA98-(7+65+4+3*(2+1))$
BA18	20468	$-1-234*56*(7-8)+9*-AB$	$BA98+7-65-4+3-21$
BA19	20469	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-(65+4)-(-3*-2+1)$
BA1A	20470	$1*2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8-9+A-B$	$BA98-7-65-4-3-2-1$
BA1B	20471	$1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8-9+A-B$	$BA98-76+5-4-(3+2)+1$
BA20	20472	$-1-2+345*6*7+89*(-A+B)$	$BA98-7-(65+4+3+2-1)$
BA21	20473	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*-4^{\wedge}5/-6)*(7+8)+9+A-B$	$BA98+7-6-54-3-21$
BA22	20474	$1-2*(3-4^{\wedge}5*-6*(-7-8)/9)+A-B$	$BA98+7+6-(54+32)-1$

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
BA23	20475	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6+7-(8+9)+A-B$	BA98+7*-6+5-43-(2-1)
BA24	20476	$-1+2-345*-6*7+89*(-A+B)$	BA98+7-65+4+3-2+1
BA25	20477	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-(7-(8-9))+A-B$	BA98-76+5-4+3-2+1
BA26	20478	$(-1+2*3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8-9+A-B$	BA98-76-5+4+3+2*1
BA27	20479	$1+2-345*-6*7-(-89+A-B)$	BA98-7-(65-4)-(-3*-2-1)
BA28	20480	$1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5/(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A-B$	BA98-(76+5)-(-4*3+2-1)
BA29	20481	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5-6+7-8+9+A-B$	BA98-(7+65)-4-(3*-2+1)
BA2A	20482	$1*2-34*(-5+6+7)*8*(-9-(A-B))$	BA98-76-5-4*3+2+1
BA2B	20483	$12-345*6*-7-8+9A-B$	BA98-76+5*(-4+3*2)-1
BA30	20484	$1+2+345*6*7-8+9-A*-B$	BA98-7-6*-54-321
BA31	20485	$-1*-2*(3-4^{\wedge}5*6*(7-8)/9)+A-B$	BA98+7+6-54-3-21
BA32	20486	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-(7-8)^{\wedge}9+A-B$	BA98+7-65-4-3-2+1
BA33	20487	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A-B$	BA98-(7-6+5)+4-3*2+1
BA34	20488	$1*2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A-B$	BA98-76+5*4-3*-2*-1
BA35	20489	$1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5*(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A-B$	BA98-7*-65-432*1
BA36	20490	$1-2-345*-6*7-(8-(9A+B))$	BA98+7-(65+4)-(-3+2)-1
BA37	20491	$-1-2*345*-6+(-7-89)*-AB$	BA98+7+6-54+3-21
BA38	20492	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-7*(8-9)+A-B$	BA98-7+6+5-43-21
BA39	20493	$-12+345*6*7+8+9A+B$	-B*(-A98+7+654)*-3*(-2+1)
BA3A	20494	$1+23*(45-67+89-A)*B$	BA98-76-5-4*-3*2+1
BA3B	20495	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*(-7-8)*9+A-B$	-B+A987-6+5-4*-321
BA40	20496	$1+2-3*(-456-7+89A)*-B$	BA98+7-6-54-3*2+1
BA41	20497	$-1-2*(3+4^{\wedge}5+67-8*-9A*-B)$	-B+A987+6-5-4*-321
BA42	20498	$(-1+2*3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8+9-(A-B)$	BA98+7-65+4-3+2+1
BA43	20499	$123+4*56*(-7+89-(A+B))$	BA98-(76-54+32+1)
BA44	20500	$1*(2+3)*-4*(-56+78*-9-AB)$	BA98-76+54-32*1
BA45	20501	$1*2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5/(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A+B$	BA98-76-5-(-4-3-21)
BA46	20502	$1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5/(6-7)^{\wedge}8+9+A+B$	BA98-(-7+65-(4+3+2))-1
BA47	20503	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5-6+7-8+9+A+B$	BA98-(7-6)-(-54-3-2+1)
BA48	20504	$(-1+2-3*4*-5)*-6*-7*8+9+A-B$	BA98-7-65-4+3+2+1
BA49	20505	$(-1+(2-3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7)*-8*9+A+B$	BA98+7-6+5*(-4-3)-21
BA4A	20506	$-1+2*3456+7*(-89-A)*-B$	BA98-(-7+6)-(-54-3+2*-1)
BA4B	20507	$-1*-2*(3-4^{\wedge}5*6*(-7-8)/9)+A+B$	BA98+76-(-5+4*-32*-1)
BA50	20508	$(-1+2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*(6-7*8)+9+A-B$	BA98-7-6+5-43+2+1
BA51	20509	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7+8*9+A-B$	BA98-(7+6)-(-54+3)+21
BA52	20510	$(-1+2*3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8-9+A-B$	BA98-(-7+6+5)-(-43-2+1)
BA53	20511	$1+2*(3-45-67+8*-9A*-B)$	BA98-7-6-5+4-(32+1)
BA54	20512	$(-1+2+3^{\wedge}4)*-5*(6-7*8)-9+A+B$	BA98-76+5-4+32-1
BA55	20513	$12+3-(-4-5+6)*7*8*(-9+AB)$	BA98-7+6*(-5+4)+32*-1
BA56	20514	$1-23*(4-567)+8*(-9+A*-B)$	BA98-76+5-4+32+1
BA57	20515	$-1/-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5-6*(-7-8+9)+A-B$	BA98-(7+6)-(-54-(3+21))
BA58	20516	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5+6*-7*(8-9))+A-B$	BA98-76+54+3-21
BA59	20517	$1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6*(-7-8)*9+A+B$	BA98+7-6+5-43+2*-1
BA5A	20518	$-1+((2-(3-4))^{\wedge}5+6*7)*8*9+A-B$	BA98+7-(65+4-3-21)
BA5B	20519	$-1-2*3*-4*-56*-7-8*9*-AB$	BA98+7+6-(-54-3-2)+1
BA60	20520	$-123*4*(5+67+8+9-AB)$	BA98+7-65-(-43+21)
BA61	20521	$1+23*4*5(-67-89)-(A-B)$	BA98-7+6-54-3+21
BA62	20522	$1*(23+4)*(567-8-9A-B)$	BA98-76-5+43-2*-1
BA63	20523	$-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*56-(7-89AB)$	BA98-7+6-(-5-4+32+1)
BA64	20524	$1*-2*(34+5-(678-9-A)*B)$	BA98-7-6-54-(-32+1)
BA65	20525	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5-6*-7+8-9+A-B$	B-A9*8-7*(-65-4)*-32*-1
BA66	20526	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-(-6-7+8)*9-(A-B)$	BA98-7-6-54+32+1
BA67	20527	$1+234*56-(7+89-A)*B$	BA98+7-6-5-(-4+32-1)
BA68	20528	$(-1+2*3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8+9+A-B$	BA98-7-65+43-2-1
BA69	20529	$1+(2+3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8+9+A-B$	BA98-(76-5)-(-43+2-1)
BA6A	20530	$-1-2*-3456-7*-89A-B$	BA98+7+6+5-(43+2)+1
BA6B	20531	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7+8*9+A+B$	BA98-76+5*4-(-32+1)
BA70	20532	$12+345*6*-7+8-(-9-AB)$	BA98-7-65+43-(-2+1)
BA71	20533	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6/(7-8)*9+A-B$	BA98-7-(-65-(-43-2))*-1
BA72	20534	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6-(-7*8+9)-(A-B)$	BA98-7-65+43+2+1
BA73	20535	$((-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7-8)+9+A+B$	BA98+7-65+4+32-1
BA74	20536	$1-234*-56-789*(-A+B)$	BA98-7+6-54+32-1
BA75	20537	$-1-2*-34*56+7+89AB$	BA98+7-65+4+32+1
BA76	20538	$-1+234*(56-7)+8+9*AB$	BA98-(76-54)-(-3+2)-1
BA77	20539	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	BA98+7-(-6-5+4+32+1)
BA78	20540	$-1*(234-56*-7)*(89-AB)$	BA98+7+6+5-4+32*-1
BA79	20541	$-1-2-34*-567-8*9AB$	BA98+7+6-54+3+21
BA7A	20542	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-(-6+7-8)*9+A-B$	BA98-(-7-(-65+43))-(-2-1))
BA7B	20543	$1-2-34*-567+8*-9AB$	-BA9-8-(-7+6543)*-2*1
BA80	20544	$-1+(2-(3-4))^{\wedge}5*(6+7+8*9)-A*B$	BA98-7+6+5-4*3*-2*-1
BA81	20545	$-1+2-34*-567+8*-9AB$	BA98-76-5-(-43-21)
BA82	20546	$((-1-2*-3*(-4-5)*6)*-7+8)*9+A-B$	BA98+7+6-(-5+43)+21
BA83	20547	$-1*-23*(456-7*(-8-9))*(-A+B)$	B-(-A-9)-(-876+543*-21)
BA84	20548	$1/((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*7)^{\wedge}8+9+A*B$	BA98-76-5+4-3*-2+1
BA85	20549	$(1-2*(-3-4^{\wedge}5))*((6-7)^{\wedge}8+9)+A-B$	BA98-7+6-5-4-(3+2*1)
BA86	20550	$1-234*(-56+7-8)-9AB$	BA98+7+6-54+32-1
BA87	20551	$(1*2+3)*4^{\wedge}(5-6+7)+8*9+A-B$	BA98-7-65-4+3*2+1
BA88	20552	$12*(-34-(-56-7-8-9AB))$	BA98+7+6-54+32+1
BA89	20553	$-123-4*(-567+89A)*-B$	BA98+76-54-32+1
BA8A	20554	$-1+2*(-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	BA98-7-6-5+4+3+2-1
BA8B	20555	$-1-234*-56-789+A+B$	BA98-7+65-4-3*2+1
BA90	20556	$1+2*(-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7+8)*9+A-B$	BA98+7+6+5*-4-3-2*-1
BA91	20557	$1-234*-56-789-(-A-B)$	BA98+7-6-5-4+3-2*1
BA92	20558	$12-(3+4*5*-678-9AB)$	BA98-(7-65)-43-21
BA93	20559	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*(-5+6-(7+8))*9+A+B$	BA98+7*-6-(-5-4)+3+2+1
BA94	20560	$-12+3*(-45-(-6+7))*(-8-9*A*-B))$	BA98-76+54-3+21
BA95	20561	$(-1*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6*(7-(8+9))+A+B$	BA98-(7-6*5)-(-43-21)
BA96	20562	$1*(23+4)*(56+78*-9*(A-B))$	BA98-7*6-(-5+4-32)+1
BA97	20563	$(-1-2)*(-3+4*-5*6)*7*8+9*A*B$	BA98-7+65+4+3*-21
BA98	20564	$-1*-2*(-3+4*-5-67+8*-9A*-B)$	BA98+7654*(-3-(-2-1))
BA99	20565	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3*-4))*-5-6*-7+8+9+A+B$	-BA9-(-8765-4321)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
BA9A	20566	$-12+3*(4+56)*(7-89)*(A-B)$	BA98-76+54+3+21
BA9B	20567	$1*(2-3)*(-45-6+7-89)*AB$	BA98+76*-5-4+321
BAA0	20568	$((-1-2*-3*(-4-5)*6)*(-7+8)*9+A+B)$	BA98+7-6+5+4-(3-(-2-1))
BAA1	20569	$(-1+2^A(-3*-4))*5-(-6-7)*8-9+A-B$	BA98+7+65-4+3*-21
BAA2	20570	$-1*(-2+34+56+78-9)*A*-B$	B*A*(98-76-(-5-4*(32+1)))
BAA3	20571	$(1-2*(-3-4^5))*((6-7)^A8+9)+A+B$	BA98-7+6-(5*4-3-21)
BAA4	20572	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5+6+7*8+9+A+B$	BA98+7-(6-5+4-3-2-1)
BAA5	20573	$(-1-2^A3)*(-4-5*(6*7+8))*9+A-B$	BA98+7-65-(-4-3*21)
BAA6	20574	$1-234*-56+7*8*(-9-A)-B$	BA98-7+6-54+3*21
BAA7	20575	$1+23-(-4*-5*-678-9AB)$	BA98-76-(-54-32+1)
BAA8	20576	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5-(-6-7)*8-9-(A-B)$	BA98-(7+6)-(-54+32+1)
BAA9	20577	$-1*-2*(-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	BA98+7-(-65-4+3*21)
BAAA	20578	$1+2*(-3*(-4-5)*-6*-7+8)*9+A+B$	BA98-7-6-(-54+32-1)
BAA8	20579	$(1+2*3)^A4*5/6/7*8*9+A-B$	BA98+7-6+5+4+3+2*1
BAB0	20580	$12*(-34+5)*(67+8-9A-B)$	BA98-7-6+5-4+3+21
BAB1	20581	$(-1-2*(-3-4^5))*(6*7+8))*9-A*B$	BA98-76-5+4*(3+21)
BAB2	20582	$-1/-2^A(-3*4)*5+(-6+7+8)*9+A+B$	BA98+7+6-5-4*-3+2*-1
BAB3	20583	$-1*2+(3+4)^A5+6^A7/8/9-A*B$	BA98+76+5-43-21
BAB4	20584	$1-2+(3+4)^A5+6^A7/8/9-A*B$	BA98-7-(-6+5)+43-21
BAB5	20585	$(-1-2^A3*(4+5))*-6*(7*8-9)+A-B$	BA98-7*-6-(-5+4-3+21)
BAB6	20586	$(-1+(-2^A3-4^5)/6)*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	BA98+76-(54+3-(-2+1))
BAB7	20587	$(-1+2^A(-3*-4))*5-((-6-7)*8-9)-A-B$	BA98-7-6+5+4-3-21
BAB8	20588	$1+2+(3+4)^A5+6^A7/8/9-A*B$	BA98+76-54-(3-2+1)
BAB9	20589	$1-2-3*-4*-5*(-6*7*8-9)-A*B$	BA98+76-54-3+2*1
BABA	20590	$-1*-2*(-3-4^5)*(6*7-8)*9-A*B$	BA98-(7-(6-5+4+3+21))
BABB	20591	$(-1+2-(3+4^5))*(-6-7)*8*9+A-B$	BA98-7-(-65+4+32+1)
BB00	20592	$1*-2*3*(45+67)*(89-AB)$	BA98-(-76+54-(3-2+1))
BB01	20593	$1+2*3*(-45-67)*(89-AB)$	BA98-7+6-5-(4-32-1)
BB02	20594	$-12*(3+4-56-(-7-8+9AB))$	BA98-7+6-(-5-43+21)
BB03	20595	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5+6*7*8*9-(A-B)$	B+A987-(-65+4*-321)
BB04	20596	$1*(2-34)*(5-(6*7-8-9*AB))$	BA98+7+65-43-(2-1)
BB05	20597	$1+(2*-3*-4+5)*-6*-7*(8+9)-A*B$	BA98+76-5-(43+2-1)
BB06	20598	$(-1+2)*3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9-(A+B)$	BA98+7+6-(5-43+21)
BB07	20599	$-12-3*4*56-(-7-8)*9AB$	BA98-7-(-65-4+32+1)
BB08	20600	$(-1+2^A3)*(-4-(5-6*7*8))*9+A-B$	BA98+7-(-65+43-2)+1
BB09	20601	$-1*23*(45-678+9+AB)$	BA98+7-6+5+4-(3+21)
BB0A	20602	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5+6+7+8-9+A*B$	BA98-7+65-(4+3+21)
BB0B	20603	$1+234*56-7*8+9*A*-B$	BA98-7+6*-5+43+21
BB10	20604	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5+6+7-(8-9)+A*B$	BA98+7+6+5+4-32+1
BB11	20605	$1-2+345*-6*-7+89+AB$	BA98-7+6+5+4+3-21
BB12	20606	$1+2+3^A(4+5)-6*(-7-8)*9+A*B$	BA98-(7-(6-5+43))-(-2+1)
BB13	20607	$-1+2-345*-6*7+89+AB$	BA98+7-6+5+4-(-3+21)
BB14	20608	$-12*(3-(45-6-7-(-8-9AB)))$	BA98-7-6+5-(-43-2)-1
BB15	20609	$(-1+(-2+3^A4)*(-5*-6+7-8))*9+A-B$	BA98-(7+6)-(5+(43-2)*-1)
BB16	20610	$-1-2*3*4*-567+8+9AB$	BA98-(7+6)-(-5-43)-(-2-1)
BB17	20611	$1*2+(-3*4)^A(5+6-7)-(-8+9)-A*B$	BA98+76+5-43+2+1
BB18	20612	$1+2+(-3*4)^A(5+6-7)-8-9-A*B$	BA98+76-54-3+21
BB19	20613	$(-1+2-(3+4^5))*(-6-7)*8*9+A+B$	BA98+7-(-6+5-4)-(-32+1)
BB1A	20614	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5-(-6-7)*8+9+A+B$	BA98+76-5-(-4+32)-1
BB1B	20615	$(-1+2^A(-3*-4))*5+6-(-7-8)*9+A-B$	BA98-(7-65-4)-32+1
BB20	20616	$-1*2+3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	BA98+76-5-(-4+32-1)
BB21	20617	$1-2-3*(4+56)*-78+9A*B$	BA98+76-5-4-3-21
BB22	20618	$-1+2*3456-7*(-89A-B)$	BA98+76-54+3+21
BB23	20619	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9+A-B$	BA98-7*6-5+43*2*-1
BB24	20620	$-1+2-3*(4-5)*(-67-8)*(9*A+B)$	BA98-(7-6)-(-5-(43+2))-1
BB25	20621	$1-234*5*-6-(-7+89)*A*-B$	-BA98+7*6-543*2*1
BB26	20622	$12*3*(-4*-5-678+9AB)$	BA98-(7+6)-(-5-(43+21))
BB27	20623	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9-(A-B)$	BA98-(-76+5)-(-43-21)
BB28	20624	$-1234-5*6*(-7*89-A-B)$	BA98+7+65+4-3-21
BB29	20625	$-1*(-2^A3*-4+5)*(-6-7*8)*9-(A+B)$	-B*(A-98+76-5-4)*-3*-21
BB2A	20626	$((1/-2+3)*(4^5+6)+7)*8-9-(A+B)$	BA98-(76-5-4)-(-32-1)
BB2B	20627	$((1-2^A3)^A4-(5-(6-7)*8))*9+A-B$	BA98+76-54-(-32+1)
BB30	20628	$1*-23*4*(-56+7-(-8+9+AB))$	BA98+7-6+5+4-3-2*-1
BB31	20629	$1+2-(-3*4)^A5/(6+7+8-9)-A*B$	BA98+7-6+5+4-3-(-2-1)
BB32	20630	$(-1*2^A3)^A4*5-(6+(-7-8)*9)+A+B$	BA98+7+65-(-4-3+21)
BB33	20631	$(-1+(-2+3^A4)*(-5*-6+7-8))*9+A+B$	BA98-7+6+5+4+3+2-1
BB34	20632	$-1-2+3^A-4*(5-6+7)^A8+9-A*B$	BA98-7-(6-5)-(-43-21)
BB35	20633	$-1*2+3^A-4*(5-6+7)^A8+9-A*B$	BA98+76-(-5*-4*(3-2)+1)
BB36	20634	$1-2+3^A-4*(5-6+7)^A8+9-A*B$	BA98-7+65-4-(-3-2+1)
BB37	20635	$1+(2-(3-4))^A5*(6+7+8*9)-(A+B)$	BA98+7-6+5+4+3+2+1
BB38	20636	$12*(3+45-(-6+7)-(8-9AB))$	BA98+7-6-5+4+3+21
BB39	20637	$(-1+2^A(-3*-4))*5+6-(-7-8)*9+A+B$	BA98-7+65-(4-3)*(-2-1)
BB3A	20638	$1-(-2+3*(-4+56)*(-78-9A))-B$	BA98-7-(-65-4+3-2-1)
BB3B	20639	$-1/-2^A-3*-4*-5*(-6-(-7-8)*9)+A-B$	BA98-(7+6*5*-4-32*-1)
BB40	20640	$-1*-2*(-3+45+67)*-8*(-9-(-A+B))$	BA98+7*-65+432+1
BB41	20641	$1^A2+3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9+A+B$	BA98-(-76-5)-(-4-3+21)
BB42	20642	$-1-23+(-4+567)*(-89+AB)$	BA98+7+65-4-3-(-2+1)
BB43	20643	$1+2+3^A(4+5)+(-6-7)*-8*9+A+B$	BA98-(7-6-5+4-3)-(-2-1)
BB44	20644	$1-23+45*6*(-7-8*9)*(-A+B)$	BA98-(7-65)-(-4-3-2)+1
BB45	20645	$-1-2-3*45*6*-7-89A*-B$	BA98+7+6+5+4+3+2-1
BB46	20646	$1+234*56-789+A*B$	BA98-(-7-65-4)+3*2*-1
BB47	20647	$-1*(-2^A3*-4+5)*(-6-7*8)*9-(A-B)$	BA98+7-(-65-4+3)+2*-1
BB48	20648	$-1+234*56-(-78+9)*A+B$	BA98-7-(6+5+43*2*-1)
BB49	20649	$((1-2^A3)^A4-(5-(-6-7)*8))*9+A+B$	BA98+76-5-4+3+2-1
BB4A	20650	$12*(-3+4*-5+6+7+8+9AB)$	BA98+7-(-6+5)*4-3*-21
BB4B	20651	$(-1-(-2*3)^A4)*5-(5-(6+7+8))+9-A*B$	BA98+76-5+4-(3-(-2+1))
BB50	20652	$-1+234*(-5+6)*7*(8-9+A)-B$	BA98-7+65-4-3+21
BB51	20653	$-1+(2-(3-4))^A5*(6+7+8*9)+A-B$	BA98+76-5+4-3-(-2-1)
BB52	20654	$(1-2^A3/-4)^A5*(6+7+8*9)+A-B$	BA98-7-6+5+4+3+2+1
BB53	20655	$-1*-23*(-4-5)*6(6-7-(-89-(A+B)))$	BA98+76+5-4-3+2+1
BB54	20656	$-1+234*56+7-8-9*A*B$	-BA98-76*(-5+4-321)

Base 12	Base 10	Increasing	Decreasing
BB55	20657	$1+(2-(3-4))^5(6+7+8*9)-(A-B)$	BA98+7-6+54-(-3-21)
BB56	20658	$-1-234*56-(7-(8-9*-A*-B))$	BA98+76-5+4+3+2*1
BB57	20659	$(-1-2^3*4*5)^*(6+(-7-8)*9)-A*B$	BA98-(-76+5-4-3-2-1)
BB58	20660	$-1-2*(-3-4*(-5-6))*-7*-8*-9+A-B$	BA98+76+5-4+3*2-1
BB59	20661	$-1*2+(-3*4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A-B$	BA98+76-(5+4*-3*(2-1))
BB5A	20662	$-1+(2^3+4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A-B$	BA98+76-5+4*-3+21
BB5B	20663	$1*(2^3+4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A-B$	BA98-7*-6-5*-4*3-2-1
BB60	20664	$-12*3*(456-789-A-B)$	BA98-7-(-6-54)-(-32+1)
BB61	20665	$-1-234*56-789+AB$	BA98-(-76-(5+4+3)+2)+1
BB62	20666	$1+2+(-3*4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A-B$	BA98+7-6-(-54-32+1)
BB63	20667	$1-234*56-789+AB$	BA98-7+65-4+32-1
BB64	20668	$1+23-4*5*(-6+7)*8*(-9A-B)$	-BA9+87+6543*-2*-1
BB65	20669	$(-1-2*(3+4^5+6))^*(7-(8+9))+A-B$	-BA9+87-6543*-2+1
BB66	20670	$-1*(-2+3)*(-4+567)*(89-AB)$	BA+9+87-654*(3-21)
BB67	20671	$-1-2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9-(A+B)$	BA98+76+5*-4+32-1
BB68	20672	$(-1-2)*(-3+4*-5*6)*7*8+9+A-B$	BA98+7*6+54-(-3+2)+1
BB69	20673	$1-2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9-A-B$	BA98+7-(6-5-43*2)+1
BB6A	20674	$1^2*(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9-A-B$	BA98+7+65+43-21
BB6B	20675	$-1+(2-(3-4))^5(6+7+8*9)+A+B$	BA98-(7-65)+4+32-1
BB70	20676	$(1-2^3/4)^5(6+7+8*9)+A+B$	BA98+76+(5-4)*-3+21
BB71	20677	$-1*(23+4)*(-567-8+9+AB)$	BA98-(-7-6-(5-(4-3))*21)
BB72	20678	$12*(34+5-(-6-(7-8+9AB)))$	BA98-(-7-6)-(-54-(32-1))
BB73	20679	$-1+2*(34+56-7)*89-A*B$	BA98-(-76-(54-32-1))
BB74	20680	$-1-(-2+((-3-4)*-5+6)*-7*8)*9+A-B$	BA98-(-7-6)-(-54-32-1)
BB75	20681	$(-1*-2+((-3-4)*-5+6)*7*8)*9+A-B$	B-A+987+6-543*-21
BB76	20682	$1-(-2+((-3-4)*-5+6)*-7*8)*9+A-B$	BA98+7+65-4-32*-1
BB77	20683	$-1*2+(-3*4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A+B$	BA98-7+65+43-2*1
BB78	20684	$12+3*45*(67+8*9-A-B)$	BA98+76-(5-(-4+32))-1
BB79	20685	$1*(2^3+4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A+B$	BA98+76+5+43-21
BB7A	20686	$1+(2^3+4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A+B$	BA98-7-(-65-43-2+1)
BB7B	20687	$1*2+(-3*4)^(5+6-7)-8*9+A+B$	BA98-7+65+43-2*-1
BB80	20688	$-1-234*56-78*9-AB$	BA98-7+65+43-(-2-1)
BB81	20689	$(-1+(-2+3^4-5*-6*7)*8)*9-A*B$	BA98-7+6*5-43*-2*1
BB82	20690	$1+234*56+78*-9-AB$	BA98+76-5-(-4-32)-1
BB83	20691	$123*(45-(-6-78)-(9+A+B))$	BA98-76+54*3+21
BB84	20692	$12*(-34-(-5+6-78)+9AB)$	BA98-(-76+5)-(-4-(32+1))
BB85	20693	$1-2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9+A-B$	BA98+76+5-4+32*1
BB86	20694	$1^2*(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9+A-B$	BA98+76+5-4+32+1
BB87	20695	$1234-(-5+67*(-89-AB))$	-BA9+8-7*(65+43)*-21
BB88	20696	$1*(2-34-56)*(-78-9A+B)$	BA98+76-(-54-(3-21))
BB89	20697	$1+2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9+A-B$	BA98+76-5-(-43+2+1)
BB8A	20698	$12345+6*-7*(89-A)+B$	BA98-(-7-(65+43-2+1))
BB8B	20699	$-1*-2*(-3-4*5)*(6*-7-8)*9+A-B$	BA98+76-5+43-2+1
BB90	20700	$1-2*(-34-5678)+9AB$	BA98+76-5-43*(-2+1)
BB91	20701	$1*2+3*4*5*(6*7*8+9)+A-B$	BA98+76-5+43+2-1
BB92	20702	$1+2+3*4*5*(6*7*8+9)+A-B$	BA98-(-76+5-43+2*-1)
BB93	20703	$(-1*-2+((-3-4)*-5+6)*7*8)*9+A+B$	BA98+76-5+43+2+1
BB94	20704	$-1+(2*-3*-4+5)*-6*-7*(8+9)+A-B$	BA98+7*(-6+5+32*-1)
BB95	20705	$1234+5-67*(-89-AB)$	BA98-7*6+(-5+43)*(-2-1)
BB96	20706	$12*(34-56-7-8*9*(-A-B))$	-B-A-9+8-7+6^5/4/3*2-1
BB97	20707	$((-1-2^3)*-4*-5+6)*-7*(8+9)-(A-B)$	BA98+76+5+43-2-1
BB98	20708	$(-1-(-2-3^4)*5)*(6*7+8)+9+A-B$	BA98+76+5-(-43-2*-1)
BB99	20709	$1*-23*(-456+7+8-9-AB)$	BA98+76+5+43-(2-1)
BB9A	20710	$1+23*(4+56+78*9-AB)$	BA98-7-(-65-(43+21))
BB9B	20711	$-12+345-(-67-89)*-A*-B$	BA98+76+54+3*-2-1
BBA0	20712	$-1+2-3*(-4-56)*(-7+89)+AB$	BA98-(-76-5)-(-43-2*1)
BBA1	20713	$-12+3+4*(567-89A)*-B$	BA98+7-6-5+4*32+1
BBA2	20714	$-1*2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9+A+B$	BA98+76+54-(-3+2)+1
BBA3	20715	$1-2+(3+4)^5+6^7/8/9+A+B$	BA98+76+54+3*(-2+1)
BBA4	20716	$-1/-2*((-3*-4)^5/6-7*8)+9+A-B$	BA98+76-(-54+3-2)-1
BBA5	20717	$-1-2/(-3*(4+5))/6^7-8-9+A-B$	-B-A98+7-6543*-2-1
BBA6	20718	$123+4*-5*-678+9AB$	BA98-7-6-54*-3-21
BBA7	20719	$-12+34*56-789*(-A-B)$	BA98-7+6+5+4*32-1
BBA8	20720	$12*-34*(5+6+78-9-AB)$	BA98-(7-6-5)-4*-32*1
BBA9	20721	$1+2+(-3*4)^(5+6-7)-8-9+A-B$	BA98-(7-6-(5+43*(2+1)))
BBAA	20722	$((1+2+3)^4+(-5-6)*7)*(8+9)+A-B$	BA98+7-6+5+4*32*1
BBAB	20723	$-1-2+3^4-4*(5-6+7)^8-9+A-B$	BA98+76+54-(-3-2*1)
BBB0	20724	$1*(-2+3)*-4*(567-89A)*B$	BA98-76-5*(-43+2-1)
BBB1	20725	$1-2+3^4-4*(5-6+7)^8-9+A-B$	BA98-(-76-(-5+43))+21
BBB2	20726	$(-1+2-3*4^5*6+7)/-8*9+A-B$	B-A98-7+6543*-2*-1
BBB3	20727	$-1+234*56+78*(-9A-B)$	BA98+7-6*(-54+32)*1
BBB4	20728	$1*2+3^4-4*(5-6+7)^8-9+A-B$	BA98-76+5*43-2+1
BBB5	20729	$1+2+3^4-4*(5-6+7)^8-9+A-B$	BA98-76*5-(-432-1)
BBB6	20730	$-1/-2*((-3*-4)^5/6+7-(8+9))+A-B$	BA98+76+5-4+3*21
BBB7	20731	$-1-2-34-567*(89-AB)$	BA98-76-(-5*43+2*-1)
BBB8	20732	$-1*-2*(-345-(-6-78*9A)-B)$	-BA*(-9-(87+65))-(-4-32-1))
BBB9	20733	$-1*2+(3+4+5)^8(-6-7+8+9)+A-B$	BA98-7*-6*5-(4-(-32+1))
BBBA	20734	$1*(2^3+4)^(5+6-7)+8-9+A-B$	BA98+7+6+5-4*-32*1
BBBB	20735	$(1+2+3)^4+5*6^7/8/9+A-B$	B+A+9+(-8-(7-6^5*4/3))*2-1